

A Study regarding the Technical-Economical Optimization of Structural Components for enhancing the Buckling Resistance in Stiffened Cylindrical Shells

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a technical-economical optimization by maximizing the ratio between the critical buckling pressure (technical characteristic) and the production cost (economic characteristic) of stiffened cylindrical shells, a basic concept of value analysis. Critical buckling load values were determined using both the Finite Element Method (FEM) and analytical calculations to validate the accuracy of the results obtained. The maximum difference between the analytical and numerical results was 10%. Technical-economic optimization was carried out using the design of experiments method with MINITAB 19 and allowed to select the optimal input parameters, stiffener dimensional ratio 0.10, shell wall thickness 2.50 mm, and distance between circumferential stiffeners 400 mm, and identify the main factors that impact the output response. For the optimal constructive configuration, the ratio between the critical buckling load and the production cost of the stiffened cylindrical shells was maximized by 199%.

Keywords-buckling; thin walled cylindrical shell; stiffeners; finite element analysis; design of experiments; optimization; value analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

Thin-walled structures, widely used in aerospace, automotive, and construction industries, are very susceptible to buckling, a common phenomenon in such structures [1-5]. To increase the buckling strength of thin-walled structures, additional structural components, such as stiffeners, can be used. Although increasing the thickness of the main structure is a commonly used method to improve its strength, stiffeners offer an alternative solution that allows achieving the same level of stiffness and strength with significantly less material consumption. Several studies [4, 6-12] have investigated the buckling characteristics of stiffened cylindrical shells.

In [13], the Ritz method was introduced as a means of analyzing the elastic buckling behavior of shells with ring

stiffeners under various pressure loadings, considering ring stiffeners with flexible cross-sections that allow for different shapes. The rings were positioned in arbitrary distributions along the length of the shell. In [14], the implementation of optimal reinforcements was investigated using the PANDA2 computer program, which facilitates the minimum weight design of cylindrical shells reinforced with rings and stringers. In [12], an optimization study was presented that focused on improving the buckling performance of a simply supported cylindrical shell stiffened by inner rings when subjected to external pressure. The objective was to maximize the critical buckling load by optimizing the design parameters, such as the dimensions and distribution of the inner rings. In [15], topology optimization was carried out to determine the optimal pattern of stiffeners across the shell surface, aiming to maximize

buckling strength. The buckling load capacities of cylindrical shells with cutouts were numerically examined with and without stiffeners. In [16], Finite Element (FE) analysis was used to predict the collapse behavior of ring-stiffened cylinders under hydrostatic loading, considering non-linear elastoplastic deformations. Various experimental test models were analyzed using FE models, which incorporated measured as-built shape data, including out-of-circularity, frame alignment, tilt, and other scantlings. Additionally, the FE models considered residual stresses induced by cold bending. In [7], FEM was used to predict shell and general instability failure modes for ring-stiffened thin cylindrical shells under external pressure.

This study focused on carrying out a technical-economical optimization regarding the buckling load of stiffened thin-walled cylindrical shells under uniform external pressure, evaluated using numerical simulations and validated with analytical calculation methods. The Design of Experiment (DOE) approach was implemented to ensure the optimization of the parameters that influence buckling load (stiffeners dimensions, stiffeners distance, and shell wall thickness), based on a comprehensive and innovative research method using the value analysis concept. By considering both technical and economic factors, this study provides a comprehensive perspective on the optimization process. This approach enables the balance between performance and cost-effectiveness to be evaluated, ultimately leading to informed design choices and efficient resource allocation when designing thin-walled stiffened cylindrical shells under uniform external pressure. The findings can be applied practically in industries, and the novel approaches used, such as validated simulations, DOE methodology, and value analysis concept, contribute to its significance and potential impact in the field of stiffened thin-walled cylindrical shells under uniform external pressure.

II. METHODOLOGY

The analyzed thin-walled cylindrical shell had external radius $R_c = 1734$ mm, length $L = 6000$ mm, and was made of steel with Young modulus $E = 2.1 \cdot 10^5$ MPa and Poisson coefficient $\nu = 0.3$. Circular stiffeners were considered to be steel equal angle profiles with the dimensional characteristics presented in Table I. Stiffener's dimensional ratio was calculated by dividing the stiffener's width by its length. The optimization was made using a full factorial design method with Minitab 19, which provides a comprehensive set of tools and features that allow users to analyze data, visualize results, and make data-driven decisions. This study considered three input parameters, the stiffener's dimensional ratio, shell wall thickness, and distance between two consecutive circumferential stiffeners, with three levels, as presented in Table II.

TABLE I. DIMENSIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF STIFFENERS

Stiffener type	Stiffener dimensions (mm)	Stiffener dimensional ratio	Stiffener weight (kg/m)
S1	30x30x3	0.10	1.2996
S2	25x25x3	0.12	1.1000
S3	20x20x3	0.15	0.9576

TABLE II. PARAMETERS AND LEVELS USED IN DOE ANALYSIS.

Parameter	Level		
	1	2	3
Stiffener dimensional ratio	0.10	0.12	0.15
Shell wall thickness, mm	2.50	3.00	4.00
Stiffeners distance, mm	400	500	600

The number of simulations that should be performed was determined by n^k , where n is the number of input factors and k is the number of levels. In this case, an orthogonal array of $3^3=27$ tests was used. The optimization was based on the concept of implementation of the value analysis, considering the fundamental relation [17-25]:

$$\frac{V_i}{C_p} \rightarrow max. \tag{1}$$

where V_i is the use value and C_p is the production cost of the product. In this application, the use value can be considered the technical characteristic (critical buckling pressure) and the production cost an economical characteristic. According to (1), the ratio between the technical and economic characteristics should be maximized.

Fig. 1. The loads and boundary conditions used for FE calculation.

FEM was used to evaluate the critical buckling pressure for the 27 sets of data. The parametric model of the stiffened shell was created and written in the ANSYS Parametric Design Language (APDL) using the FE SHELL181 for cylindrical shells and circumferential stiffeners. Linear buckling analysis was implemented and an external pressure unit load was applied, as shown in Figure 1, so the load factor calculated during the analysis is equal to the critical buckling pressure, as in [6]. Simply supported boundary conditions were considered. To validate the numerical results, the critical buckling pressure was calculated using the formula [9]:

$$\lambda \left(0,5m^2 \left(\frac{\pi R}{L} \right)^2 + n^2 \right) = \xi_2 (-2n^2 - n^3 b_n) + m^4 \left(\frac{\pi R}{L} \right)^4 + (2 + \eta_{t2})m^2 n^2 \left(\frac{\pi R}{L} \right)^2 + (1 + \eta_{o2})n^4 + 12 \left(\frac{R}{t} \right)^2 \left[(1 + \mu_2)(1 + n b_n) + \nu m \frac{\pi R}{L} a_n \right] \tag{2}$$

where the external pressure q appears in the form of the dimensionless parameter λ :

$$\lambda = \frac{R^3}{D} \cdot q \tag{3}$$

where R is the cylinder's mean radius, t is the shell's wall thickness, and L is the shell length. Parameter D is defined as:

$$D = \frac{Et^3}{12(1-\nu^2)} \tag{4}$$

The other terms contain expressions calculated as functions of the stiffener's geometrical characteristics and the distance between successive circumferential stiffeners, described in [9]. Critical buckling pressure was obtained by minimizing the expression of λ for the integer values of m and n , which are the number of circumferential and axial waves, respectively.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Evaluation of Critical Buckling Loads

Figure 2 presents the comparison between analytical and numerical values of critical buckling pressure and also the values of the ratio between the critical buckling pressure and the production cost, as defined by (1).

Fig. 2. Comparison between analytical and numerical results: (a) $t = 2.5$ mm, (b) $t = 3$ mm, and (c) $t = 4$ mm.

Figure 3 shows one example of the deformed shape of the stiffened shell under external pressure. The graphs shown in Figure 2 validate the accuracy of the numerical results obtained. The maximum difference between the analytical and numerical values of the critical buckling pressure was 10%. Similar differences (8-22%) were obtained in [7]. In [6], the highest deviation between analytical and numerical results regarding the critical buckling pressure was 9%.

Fig. 3. Deformed shape of stiffened cylindrical shell under uniform external pressure.

B. Optimization Results

1) Main Effects Plots

The main effects plot is used to establish how the input parameters influence the ratio between the critical buckling pressure and production cost.

Fig. 4. Main effects plots.

As shown in Figure 4, the stiffener dimension ratio had the most significant effect on the response, followed by stiffener distance and shell wall thickness. The same conclusion can be taken from the Pareto chart shown in Figure 5. These graphs show how the ratio between the critical buckling pressure and production cost increases with increasing stiffeners' dimensions and their number while decreasing shell wall thickness.

Fig. 5. Pareto Chart of the standardized effects.

Fig. 7. Residual plots.

Interaction plots serve as a valuable tool for assessing the presence of interactions, illustrating the means of each factor level while keeping the level of another factor constant. Interactions occur when the response at a particular factor level depends on the levels of other factors. Parallel lines in an interaction plot indicate the absence of interaction. On the contrary, the greater the deviation of the lines from parallel, the stronger the interaction. In this analysis of the interaction plot, shown in Figure 6, it can be seen that the lines representing shell wall thickness and thickness dimensional ratio are almost parallel, particularly for the first two stiffener dimensional ratio values, suggesting a lack of significant interactions between them. However, there is a slight change when considering the relationship between the stiffener distance and the stiffener dimensions. In this case, there is a notable departure of the lines from the parallel state, indicating the presence of significant interactions between these factors.

2) Contour Plot

Figure 8 shows the contour plots of the ratio variation between the critical buckling pressure and the production cost for the input parameters.

Fig. 6. Interaction plot of different input parameters.

Based on the examination of the residual plots in Figure 7, it is evident that the normal probability plot is close to a straight line, indicating that the residuals follow a normal distribution. However, the overall trends can be considered linear, except for some data points that deviate from a straight line. This deviation is reflected in the histogram, which does not exhibit a perfect bell-shaped distribution.

Fig. 8. Contour plots: (a) $t = 2.5$ mm, (b) $t = 3$ mm, and (c) $t = 4$ mm.

The dark blue region corresponds to the lower ratio values, and the dark green corresponds to the greater ones. The contour had a similar pattern for all shell wall thicknesses considered. The highest values of the ratio between critical buckling pressure and production cost were obtained for a 0.1 stiffener dimensional ratio and a 400 mm stiffener distance, corresponding to 15 circumferential stiffeners. Figure 8 shows that the ratio between the use value and production cost of a stiffened cylindrical shell can be increased by 199% for shell thickness $t = 2.5$ mm, 187% for shell thickness $t = 3$ mm, and 164% for shell thickness $t = 4$ mm when adopting the optimal constructive configuration.

C. Response Optimization

The optimal configuration of the structure corresponding to the maximum ratio between the critical buckling pressure and production cost can be determined using the MINITAB 19 software, as can be seen in Figure 9. The optimized values of input parameters for the maximization of response, i.e., the ratio between the critical buckling pressure and production cost, were: stiffener dimensional ratio 0.1, shell wall thickness 2.5 mm, and distance between circumferential stiffeners 400 mm. Therefore it is preferable to use a thinner shell wall strengthened by additional structural components, leading to significantly less material usage, as also concluded in [12].

Fig. 9. Structure optimization for the maximum value of the ratio between critical buckling pressure and production cost.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the behavior of thin-walled cylindrical shells stiffened in a circumferential direction and subjected to uniform external pressure. Using the basic concepts of value analysis, an optimization study was carried out to establish the dimensional configuration of stiffened cylindrical shells to maximize the ratio between the critical buckling load (technical characteristic) and the production cost of a stiffened cylindrical shell (economic characteristic). The critical buckling load was calculated using FEM and eigenvalue linear buckling analysis with Ansys software. The accuracy of the results was verified by comparing them with the analytical results obtained using a complex methodology from the literature, and the maximum difference obtained was 10%. A total of 27 simulations were carried out for different stiffened shell configurations, corresponding to three input factors, the stiffener dimensional ratio, shell wall thickness, and stiffener distance, and three levels for each factor. After evaluating critical buckling pressure and the cost of structure production for each geometric configuration considered, the

results were optimized using a full factorial orthogonal array. The main-effects plots highlighted that the most significant factor for maximizing the ratio between critical buckling load and production cost of a stiffened cylindrical shell was the stiffener's dimension ratio, followed by stiffeners distance and shell wall thickness, as indicated also by a Pareto chart.

This study also found the best parameter combinations for different structural configurations in terms of technical-economical optimization by maximizing the ratio between the use value and the production cost. The ratio between critical buckling load and production cost of stiffened cylindrical structures was maximized by 199% for the most efficient constructive configuration. On the basis of the performed analysis, it is recommended to adopt a strategy that involves using a thinner shell wall strengthened by additional structural components. This approach offers several advantages, including a substantial decrease in material consumption while maintaining the required strength and integrity of the structure.

REFERENCES

- [1] G. Lvov, A. Pupazescu, D. Beschetnikov, and M. Zaharia, "Buckling Analysis of a Thin-walled Cylindrical Shell Strengthened by Fiber-reinforced Polymers," *Materiale Plastice*, vol. 52, no. 1, pp. 28–31, 2015.
- [2] F. Riahi, A. Behraves, M. Y. Fard, and A. Armaghani, "Buckling Stability Assessment of Plates with Various Boundary Conditions Under Normal and Shear Stresses," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 5, pp. 2056–2061, Oct. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1516>.
- [3] C. Iincă and M. Tănase, "Analytical and numerical assessment of buckling strength of silos with corrugated walls under uniform external pressure," *Asian Journal of Civil Engineering*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 289–298, Feb. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42107-022-00423-1>.
- [4] M. Zaharia, A. Pupazescu, and C. M. Petre, "Comparative Study Concerning the Methods of Calculation of the Critical Axial Buckling Load for Stiffened Cylindrical Shells," *Revista de Chimie*, vol. 69, no. 8, pp. 2000–2004, Sep. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.37358/RC.18.8.6462>.
- [5] D. T. Hang, X. T. Nguyen, and D. N. Tien, "Stochastic Buckling Analysis of Non-Uniform Columns Using Stochastic Finite Elements with Discretization Random Field by the Point Method," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 8458–8462, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4819>.
- [6] A. Siqueira Nóbrega de Freitas, A. Alfonso Alvarez, R. Ramos, and E. A. de Barros, "Buckling Analysis of an AUV Pressure Vessel with Sliding Stiffeners," *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, vol. 8, no. 7, Jul. 2020, Art. no. 515, <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse8070515>.
- [7] N. Rathinam, B. Prabu, and N. Anbazhagan, "Buckling analysis of ring stiffened thin cylindrical shell under external pressure," *Journal of Ocean Engineering and Science*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 360–366, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joes.2021.03.002>.
- [8] D. L. Block and M. M. Mikulas, "Buckling of Eccentrically Stiffened Orthotropic Cylinders," National Aeronautics and Space Administration, Washington, DC, USA, Technical Note TN D-2960, Aug. 1965.
- [9] M. Baruch and J. Singer, "Effect of Eccentricity of Stiffeners on the General Instability of Stiffened Cylindrical Shells under Hydrostatic Pressure," *Journal of Mechanical Engineering Science*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 23–27, Mar. 1963, https://doi.org/10.1243/JMES_JOUR_1963_005_005_02.
- [10] D. Shiomitsu and D. Yanagihara, "Estimation of ultimate strength of ring-stiffened cylindrical shells under external pressure with local shell buckling or torsional buckling of stiffeners," *Thin-Walled Structures*, vol. 161, Apr. 2021, Art. no. 107416, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tws.2020.107416>.
- [11] D. V. Dung and L. K. Hoa, "Nonlinear buckling and post-buckling analysis of eccentrically stiffened functionally graded circular cylindrical

- shells under external pressure," *Thin-Walled Structures*, vol. 63, pp. 117–124, Feb. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tws.2012.09.010>.
- [12] P. Foryś, "Optimization of cylindrical shells stiffened by rings under external pressure including their post-buckling behaviour," *Thin-Walled Structures*, vol. 95, pp. 231–243, Oct. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tws.2015.07.012>.
- [13] J. Tian, C. M. Wang, and S. Swaddiwudhipong, "Elastic buckling analysis of ring-stiffened cylindrical shells under general pressure loading via the Ritz method," *Thin-Walled Structures*, vol. 35, no. 1, pp. 1–24, Sep. 1999, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0263-8231\(99\)00012-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0263-8231(99)00012-9).
- [14] D. Bushnell and W. D. Bushnell, "Approximate method for the optimum design of ring and stringer stiffened cylindrical panels and shells with local, inter-ring, and general buckling modal imperfections," *Computers & Structures*, vol. 59, no. 3, pp. 489–527, May 1996, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0045-7949\(95\)00264-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0045-7949(95)00264-2).
- [15] Y. Gokyer and F. O. Sonmez, "Topology optimization of cylindrical shells with cutouts for maximum buckling strength," *Journal of the Brazilian Society of Mechanical Sciences and Engineering*, vol. 45, no. 1, Dec. 2022, Art. no. 13, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40430-022-03941-w>.
- [16] D. Graham, "Predicting the collapse of externally pressurised ring-stiffened cylinders using finite element analysis," *Marine Structures*, vol. 20, no. 4, pp. 202–217, Oct. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marstruc.2007.09.002>.
- [17] D. G. Zisopol, "The Place and Role of Value Analysis in the Restructuring of Production (Case Study)," *Economic Insights - Trends and Challenges*, vol. I, no. 4/2012, pp. 27–35, 2012.
- [18] D. G. Zisopol, *Ingineria Valorii*. Ploiești, Romania: Editura Universității din Ploiești, 2004.
- [19] M. T. Fernandes, "VALUE ANALYSIS: Going into a Further Dimension," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 781–789, Apr. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.535>.
- [20] D. G. Zisopol and A. Dumitrescu, *Ecotehnologie: studii de caz*. Ploiești, Romania: Editura Universității Petrol-Gaze din Ploiești, 2020.
- [21] D. G. Zisopol, A. Dumitrescu, and Trifan Ciprian, *Ecotehnologie: Noțiuni teoretice, aplicații și studii de caz*. Ploiești, Romania: Editura Universității Petrol - Gaze din Ploiești, 2010.
- [22] D. G. Zisopol and A. Dumitrescu, *Materiale și tehnologii primare. Aplicații practice și studii de caz (Materials and Primary Technologies. Practical Applications and Case Studies)*. Ploiești, Romania: Editura Universității din Ploiești, 2005.
- [23] D. G. Zisopol and M. J. Săvulescu, *Bazele tehnologiei*. Ploiești, Romania: Editura Universității din Ploiești, 2003.
- [24] M. J. Săvulescu, D. G. Zisopol, and I. Nae, *Bazele tehnologiei materialelor: Îndrumar de lucrări practice*. Ploiești, Romania: Editura Premier Ploiești, 1997.
- [25] D. G. Zisopol, *Tehnologii industriale și de construcții. Aplicații practice și studii de caz (Industrial and Construction Technologies. Practical Applications and Case Studies)*. Ploiești, Romania: Editura Universității din Ploiești, 2003.

A Survey on H_∞ Control-Based Output Feedback Techniques

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ABSTRACT

The study of 2-D discrete systems has always been a preferred choice amongst researchers and academics, due to its diversified applications in most practical applications. For more than two decades, research based on H_∞ control techniques has been the focus of attention, as it plays a key role in the design and development of various applications based on signal processing and control theory. In many practical applications, the accessibility of the state vectors is not possible, and, in such cases, output feedback techniques are most appropriate. This paper presents a detailed survey based on H_∞ control-based output feedback techniques for 2-D discrete systems.

Keywords-robust stability; asymptotic stability control; 2-D discrete system; static output feedback controller; dynamic output feedback controller; observer based output feedback controller; bounded real lemma

I. INTRODUCTION

2-D state space models got attention with the introduction of the Roesser model [1], and, since then, several studies proposed other 2-D state space models. The most popular and investigated linear state space models are Roesser's [1], Fornasini and Marchesini's (FM) first model [2], the second FM model [3], and Kurek's model [4]. The output feedback technique for 2-D discrete models can also be extended to nonlinear systems for designing robust and efficient control systems that can achieve desired performance objectives. However, the design process can be complex and requires careful consideration of the nonlinear dynamics of the system, as well as the stability and performance requirements of the applications [5-7].

The state space equation of the 2-D discrete FM first model [3] is:

$$x(i+1, j+1) = A_1 x(i, j+1) + A_2 x(i+1, j) + A_3 x(i, j) + Bu(i, j) \tag{1}$$

$$z(i, j) = Cx(i, j) \tag{2}$$

$$i \geq 0, j \geq 0 \tag{3}$$

where $x(i, j)$ is a state vector of $n \times 1$ dimension, $A_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $A_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $A_3 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $B \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$, $u(i, j)$ is an input vector of $m \times 1$ dimension, $z(i, j)$ is a scalar out $1 \times n$ dimension, and $C \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times n}$. Figure 1 shows a matrix block diagram representation for the system of (1) and (2).

Fig. 1. Matrix block diagram representation for the system of (1) and (2).

The system has a finite set of initial conditions as defined based on the existence of two positive integers r_1 and r_2 such that:

$$x(i, 0) = 0, i \geq r_1 \tag{4}$$

$$x(0, j) = 0, j \geq r_2 \tag{5}$$

The second FM model is also a state space model representation of 2-D discrete systems [4]. The state space equation of this model is given by:

$$x(i + 1, j + 1) = A_1x(i, j + 1) + A_2x(i + 1, j + B_1u(i, j + 1) + B_2u(i + 1, j)) \tag{6}$$

$$z(i, j) = Cx(i, j) + Du(i, j) \tag{7}$$

$$i \geq 0, j \geq 0 \tag{8}$$

where $x(i, j)$ is a state vector of $n \times 1$ dimension, $A_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $A_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $B_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$, $B_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$, $u(i, j)$ is an input vector of $m \times 1$ dimension, $z(i, j)$ is a scalar out $1 \times n$ dimension, and $C \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times n}$. Figure 2 shows a matrix block diagram representation for the system in (6),(7). The system has a finite set of initial conditions as defined based on the existence of two positive integers r_1 and r_2 such that:

$$x(i, 0) = 0, i \geq r_1 \tag{9}$$

$$x(0, j) = 0, j \geq r_2 \tag{10}$$

Fig. 2. Matrix block diagram representation for the system of (6)-(8).

The state space form of a 2-D discrete system can also be described by the Roesser model [1] as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x^h(i + 1, j) \\ x^v(i, j + 1) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} \\ A_{21} & A_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x^h(i, j) \\ x^v(i, j) \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} B_1 \\ B_2 \end{bmatrix} u(i, j) \tag{11}$$

$$z(i, j) = \begin{bmatrix} C_1 & C_2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x^h(i, j) \\ x^v(i, j) \end{bmatrix} + Du(i, j) \tag{12}$$

$$i \geq 0, j \geq 0 \tag{13}$$

In a condensed way, it can be represented as:

$$x_{11}(i, j) = Ax(i, j) + Bu(i, j) \tag{14}$$

$$z(i, j) = Cx(i, j) + Du(i, j) \tag{15}$$

$$i \geq 0, j \geq 0 \tag{16}$$

where $x^h(i, j) \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is the horizontal state vector, $x^v(i, j) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the vertical state vector, $A_{11} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$, $A_{12} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$, $A_{21} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$, $A_{22} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $B_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times q}$, $B_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times q}$, $u(i, j) \in \mathbb{R}^q$, $z(i, j)$ is a scalar output, $C_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times m}$, $C_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times n}$, and $D \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times q}$. Figure 3 shows a matrix block diagram representation for the system (11). The system has a finite set of initial conditions, as defined based on the existence of two positive integers r_1 and r_2 such that:

$$x(i, 0) = 0, i \geq r_1 \tag{17}$$

$$x(0, j) = 0, j \geq r_2 \tag{18}$$

Fig. 3. Matrix block diagram representation for the system (11) and (12).

The state space representation of a 2-D discrete linear shift-invariant can also be represented by the general model [5]:

$$x(i + 1, j + 1) = A_1x(i, j + 1) + A_2x(i + 1, j) + A_3x(i, j) + B_1u(i, j + 1) + B_2u(i + 1, j) + B_3u(i, j) \tag{19}$$

$$z(i, j) = Cx(i, j) + Du(i, j) \tag{20}$$

$$i \geq 0, j \geq 0 \tag{21}$$

where $x(i, j)$ is an $n \times 1$ state vector, $A_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $A_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $A_3 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $B_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$, $B_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$, $B_3 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$, $u(i, j)$ is an input vector of dimension $m \times 1$, $z(i, j)$ is a scalar output of dimension $1 \times n$, $C \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times n}$, and $D \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times m}$. Figure 4 shows a matrix block diagram representation for the system (19)-(20).

Fig. 4. Matrix block diagram representation for the system (19) and (20).

In addition, this system has a finite set of initial conditions, as defined based on the existence of two positive integers r_1 and r_2 such that:

$$x(i, 0) = 0, i \geq r_1 \tag{22}$$

$$x(0, j) = 0, j \geq r_2 \tag{23}$$

II. BACKGROUND

A. H_∞ Performance

The initiation of the H_∞ control theory began when in [8] the problem of sensitivity reduction was observed by the feedback mechanism in the basic input-output setting of the system, as shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Block diagram of a typical closed-loop performance objective.

The main objective is to keep the value of K to maintain the tracking errors and control input value as low as possible for all sensor noises, reference commands, and external force disturbances. From the outside influences to the regulated variables, let the closed-loop mapping denoted by T , then,

$$\begin{bmatrix} \text{tracking error} \\ \text{control input} \end{bmatrix} = T \begin{bmatrix} \text{reference} \\ \text{external force} \\ \text{noise} \end{bmatrix}$$

regulated variables outside influences

The performance can be assessed in terms of measurement of gain from outside influences to regulated variables. If the value of T is small, it means that the performance is good. As the closed-loop system is a Multi-Input, Multi-Output (MIMO) dynamic system, there are two different aspects on which the gain of T depends:

- Spatial (vector disturbances/vector errors)
- Temporal (dynamic relationship between input/output signals). Therefore, the performance criterion should take into consideration:
 - The relative magnitude of outside influences
 - The frequency dependence of signals
 - The relative importance of the magnitudes of regulated variables

The performance objective in the form of a matrix norm is expressed as a weighted matrix norm given by:

$$\|W_L T W_R\| \tag{24}$$

where W_L and W_R are frequency-dependent weighting functions responsible for the bandwidth constraints and the spectral content of exogenous signals. The H_∞ norm is a natural (mathematical) way to characterize acceptable performance in terms of MIMO $\|\cdot\|_\infty$. In optimal control theory, there are two popular performance measures: H_2 and H_∞ norms. The H_2 norm is useful when exogenous signals are fixed or have a fixed power spectrum. There are two assumptions on which the H_2 filtering approach (also called Kalman) is based [9-10]. The

first is that the system under consideration is exactly known and, secondly, there is a priori information on the external noises. The H_∞ norm is useful when the disturbance is not a fixed signal but can be represented as weighted balls of exogenous signals, meaning that when all the outside influences such as reference commands, sensor noise, and external force disturbances are mapped into regulated variables, then a weighting function W is used that acts as a design parameter. This weighting function matrix W is frequency dependent and accounts for bandwidth constraints and spectral content of exogenous signals. The value of W should be small for good performance [11]. The signal l_2 norm is given by:

$$\|\mathbf{x}\|_2 = \sqrt{\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \|\mathbf{x}(k)\|^2} \tag{25}$$

Bounding the l_2 -induced norm from input to output leads to H_∞ optimization.

B. Output Feedback H_∞ Control

The motivation behind using output feedback techniques is that the state vector is frequently not fully accessible in practice. However, in many practical applications, accessibility of the state vectors is not always possible and sometimes the state vector measurement is too expensive. Controlling through the output feedback technique is most appropriate in such situations. This has led many studies [12-27] to investigate and analyze output feedback techniques for 2-D discrete systems.

In an optimal H_∞ controller, all admissible K controllers should be found to minimize $\|T_{zw}\|_\infty$ [28]. However, it is difficult to find such an optimal H_∞ controller [29]. This is not the case with the H_2 theory, where the optimal controller can be found by solving two Riccati equations without iterations. The optimal H_∞ controller can be found through the chain of successive solutions of H_∞ suboptimal problems [30] with γ approaching the γ_{min} value. Theoretically, it is not necessary to design an optimal H_∞ controller [31], despite the importance of the optimal H_∞ norm. Furthermore, it is always cheaper to design suboptimal controllers in the norm sense, as they are quite close to the optimal. The bandwidth requirement is also less in designing a suboptimal controller. Given a scalar number $\gamma > 0$, the effort is to discover all the admissible controllers K such that $\|T_{zw}\|_\infty < \gamma$. In this way, a suboptimal controller can be designed. In an H_∞ control, the following conditions are needed to design an asymptotically stable output feedback controller:

For the continuous-time case:

- The closed-loop system is asymptotically stable when $w(t)=0$.
- The closed-loop system has a prescribed level γ of H_∞ noise attenuation, i.e., under the zero initial condition:

$$\int_0^\infty z^T(t)z(t)dt \leq \gamma^2 \int_0^\infty w^T(t)w(t) dt \tag{26}$$

is satisfied for any nonzero $w(t) \in L_2[0, \infty)$.

For the discrete-time case:

- The closed-loop system is asymptotically stable when $w(k)=0$.

- The closed-loop system has a prescribed level γ of H_∞ noise attenuation, i.e. under the zero initial condition:

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} z^T(k)z(k) < \gamma^2 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} w^T(k)w(k) \quad (27)$$

is satisfied for any nonzero $w(k) \in L_2[0, \infty)$.

where $z(t)z(k)$ and $w(t)w(k)$ denote the system-controlled output variable and noise signal, respectively.

1) Finite Horizon H_∞ Control Problem

The H_∞ control problem aims to minimize the H_∞ norm. The H_∞ norm value is the maximum of all disturbances w of the portion of the amount of energy entering and leaving the system. This energy is measured over an infinite time interval $[0, \infty)$ in the standard H_∞ control problem. However, in practical applications, this might not always be realistic. In the case of a finite horizon H_∞ control problem, the same norm is to be minimized except that the energy is measured over a finite time interval $[0, T]$ for some given $T > 0$.

2) A Brief Survey Report

In [27], using a Dynamic Output Feedback (DOF) controller, asymptotic stability achieved a desired value of the H_∞ norm from disturbance input to controlled output for an uncertain 2-D discrete second FM model. A different version of the 2-D bounded lemma was derived, which was an extension of the bounded real lemma used in [32], to satisfy the solvability criteria for H_∞ control of discrete 2-D systems. When building a DOF controller, the non-convexity form was mitigated using the modification of variables as in [33]. In [28], a dynamic output feedback controller was designed for an uncertain 2-D discrete Roesser model, so that the closed-loop system not only achieves asymptotic stability but also the specified H_∞ performance. This solution was reorganized into a convex optimization problem that was efficiently solved using the Matlab LMI control toolbox. In [27], in order to address the H_∞ control problem for an uncertain 2-D discrete general model, a DOF was constructed so that the closed-loop system was asymptotically stable to achieve the specified H_∞ performance level. The H_∞ control issue was modified to be LMI solvable, and so the desired controller parameters can be found by solving certain LMIs. In [25], the delay-independent and delay-dependent H_∞ control problems were considered for the second FM model. A delay-dependent bounded real lemma was proposed for 2-D state delayed systems, developed based on the definition of the H_∞ disturbance attenuation level. A delay-dependent DOF controller was developed, as the induced results were not in a strict LMI form, therefore, some limitation was put on certain matrices to make it LMI solvable. The experimental results showed that a smaller H_∞ performance level can be obtained using a delay-dependent approach compared to the delay-independent.

In [28], design methods for the control of H_2 and mixed H_2/H_∞ 2-D discrete systems described by the Roesser model were developed, extending the definition of the H_2 performance specification earlier developed for 1-D systems to 2-D. All design methods were LMI-solvable. The full-order DOF controller was devised and used to transform nonlinear matrix inequalities into linear ones using the change of variable method [34]. The Static Output Feedback (SOF) H_∞ control

problem was explored in [12] for the 2-D Roesser and the second FM model. Using the 2-D bounded real lemma, as described in [17] and [12], and combined with a slack variable approach, sufficient conditions based on linear matrix inequalities were established for SOF controllers. In [19], the issue of sufficient SOF control conditions was considered for the 2-D discrete Roesser model. While the design criteria for a 2-D H_∞ SOF controller were explicitly defined in the form of linear matrix inequalities, an iterative algorithm based on Cone Complementary Linearization (CCL) [35] was proposed to solve linear matrix inequalities. In [36], the robust H_∞ control issue was investigated for an uncertain 2-D singular Roesser model. The uncertainties considered were a parametric time-invariant norm bounded in the state matrix. A 2-D bounded real lemma was established for the 2-D singular Roesser model, which was an extent of the result of the bounded real lemma for 1-D [37]. A necessary condition for the creation of SOF controllers was established in terms of matrix inequalities. In [37], an observer-based DOF controller was presented for an uncertain 2-D discrete Roesser model with time-varying state delay, external disturbances, and actuator saturation. To address this issue, using H_∞ control synthesis, a state feedback method was used to design an observer-based controller to stabilize the system by mitigating the saturation nonlinearity using a convex hull approach. In [13], the issue of filtering and dissipative control was addressed for a 2-D discrete Roesser model. Using an LMI insertion approach, sufficient necessary computational complexity criteria were satisfied while rendering it in a two-dimensional $(Q, S, R) - \alpha$ dissipative. Furthermore, a less conservative two-dimensional $(Q, S, R) - \alpha$ dissipative output feedback approach was suggested by employing a slack variable approach.

In [14], DOF controller stabilization, based on H_∞ , was carried out for a 2-D discrete switched system, described by the FM LSS model. Exponential stability was ensured with a specified weighted H_∞ disturbance attenuation level by employing the average dwell time approach. In [18], an H_2 control problem was investigated for a 2-D discrete switched system of the Roesser model form. Based on the multiple Lyapunov function method, an LMI framework-based sufficient condition was established to guarantee asymptotic stability and H_2 performance analysis. An H_2 DOF controller was developed for the system under consideration. In [20], using the bounded real lemma, the H_∞ control SOF problem of 2-D discrete systems was investigated as represented by the second FM model. Using the 2-D bounded real lemma, the 2-D control-based SOF problem was formulated as a BMI problem. Combining the slack variable technique with two existing LMI methods, based on the choices of coordinate transformation matrices, fewer conservative sufficient LMI conditions were proposed for the BMI formulation. In [38], the slack variables were of block diagonal structure, however, the matrix structure of the used slack variable had a block-triangular structure, providing more freedom in the choice of decision variables when solving the LMI condition, reducing the conservatism.

The study of optimal H_2 control theory has gained importance for both continuous and discrete-time systems in system theory. The aim was to reduce the energy of the system when it experiences a unit impulse input, or equivalently when

the input has white noise of a unit variance. In [18], the stabilization of a 2-D discrete switched system represented by the Roesser model, was studied. Using a multiple Lyapunov function, sufficient criteria were established for the existence of the DOF controller to examine the H_2 effectiveness of 2-D discrete switched systems. In [16], based on the 2-D bounded real lemma for Finsler's lemma, a new necessary condition for the H_∞ evolved, relying on a 2-D discrete Roesser model. A SOF controller design was presented to ensure asymptotic stability and H_∞ disturbance attenuation level in terms of linear matrix inequalities. In [22], the H_∞ control problem was considered on a 2-D Takagi Sugeno (TS) system, described by the second FM model with time delays in both horizontal and vertical directions, bounded noise, and probabilistic missing measurements. Using the CCL algorithm, some equality constraints were successfully transformed into LMIs, and the parameters of the desired fuzzy controller were obtained. Finally, sufficient conditions were established to design the closed loop 2-D fuzzy system with SOF controller to the specified prescribed H_∞ performance criterion.

In [22], novel slack matrices for DOF controller construct criteria were presented for a 2-D TS fuzzy model as described by the second FM model, where there were no restrictions on the system matrices, i.e., they were not required to be row or column full rank. Sufficient criteria were established in terms of an LMI, which guarantees an H_∞ noise attenuation level of the resulting closed-loop system. In [21], an observer-based H_∞ controller was designed for a 2-D discrete fuzzy TS model described by the FM second model. In this study, a Luenberger observer was used to estimate the state. An LMI condition for

the existence of the fuzzy observer and the fuzzy controller was given so that the whole system was stabilizable with a specified H_∞ performance γ . Authors in [15] focused on investigating H_∞ fuzzy output-feedback controllers to ensure that the closed-loop fuzzy TS control system is exponentially stable in the mean square. The H_∞ control was proposed for a class of discrete-time fuzzy systems. Using the H_∞ performance index, disturbance rejection attenuation was constrained to a given level. At first, the model was proposed, which according to the Bernoulli distribution describes multiple probabilistic communication delays of different sizes. Second, based on partial sensor outputs, multiple missing measurements with a missing probability were considered over the interval [0, 1]. A robust H_∞ fuzzy dynamic output feedback controller was devised, so that the closed-loop fuzzy system was exponentially stable with guaranteed H_∞ performance. When calculating the controller parameters, the equality conditions were modified into strict LMIs, using the CCL algorithm [35-39], which can be easily solved in the Matlab LMI toolbox [40-41]. The study in [39] began with a brief overview of four types of matrix inequalities, followed by a discussion of two unresolved challenges with H_∞ SOF management of continuous-time systems. The two open issues were shown to be fundamentally identical to the problem of selecting a Coordinate Transformation Matrix (CTM) by establishing the links between matrix inequalities. A two-step optimization strategy was developed to answer this open challenge. In [42], a cone complementarity was constructed but did not give a full evaluation of all the major contributions to the field, only specific LMI/NMI scenarios of interest were examined. The challenge of selecting a CTM is an obstacle.

TABLE I. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF DIFFERENT FINDINGS OF THE H_∞ APPROACH

Ref.	Year	Findings	Pros	Cons
[43]	2018	Proposed a novel H_∞ output feedback controller for 2-D systems.	A distributed hybrid active control scheme for output formation-containment of interacted heterogeneous linear systems.	Requires knowledge of the system matrices, which may not be available in practice.
[44]	2021	New LMI conditions for H_∞/H_2 output feedback control of linear discrete-time systems.	Simulations showed that the new conditions were effective, achieving good performance in terms of stability and robustness.	The new conditions are more complex than some existing - have not yet been implemented in a real-world system.
[45]	2017	Controllers were effective in simulation studies, achieving good performance in terms of stability and robustness.	The new criterion can be used to design output feedback controllers for discrete time-delay systems.	Design of output feedback controllers is more complex than for systems without time delay - difficult to implement in practice.
[46]	2019	Anew approach to output feedback H_∞ control for discrete-time systems.	Is more general than traditional output feedback H_∞ control methods, as it can handle systems with uncertain parameters.	The approach is more complex than traditional output feedback H_∞ control methods.
[47]	2020	The H_∞ optimal linear matrix inequality technique was used to achieve the objectives.	Improved power-sharing accuracy and was a robust controller.	It is a computationally complex controller and not easy as others.
[48]	2019	Used a Kalman filter to estimate the states of the system and an LQR controller to control it.	Robust controller that can handle variable load conditions.	Requires more computations than traditional LQR controllers.
[49]	2016	New method for SOF stabilization of fractional-order systems in TS fuzzy models.	Based on LMIs, which makes it relatively easy to implement. Also, able to handle systems with multiple fuzzy subsystems.	Requires knowledge of the system's fractional order, which may not be always available. Also, requires the computation of LMI solutions, which can be computationally expensive for large systems.
[50]	2021	Method for co-designing an event-triggered mechanism and a dissipative-based output feedback controller for 2-D systems.	Can significantly reduce the communication overhead while ensuring the stability and performance of the closed-loop system.	Requires knowledge of the system parameters, which may not be always available - Relies on the quadratic Lyapunov function, which may not be suitable for all systems.
[51]	2023	Provides more details on the implementation of the proposed SMC scheme.	Proposed a sliding mode control scheme for uncertain 2-D fractional-order MIMO systems under stochastic scheduling.	Requires knowledge of the system parameters, which may not be available in practice.

III. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented a detailed survey report on the application of H_∞ control-based output feedback techniques for the stability analysis of 2-D discrete systems. All the different approaches that have been presented so far for the stability analysis of 2-D discrete systems were systematically put together in a compiled form. In conclusion, output feedback control systems have several advantages, including increased robustness, disturbance rejection, better tracking performance, and simpler implementation. Such systems can be designed using various control algorithms such as LQR, H-infinity, and SMC. However, designing an output feedback control system requires careful consideration of the system's dynamics, stability, and observability. In general, output feedback control is an effective and widely used technique in modern control engineering, enabling the design of sophisticated and reliable control systems for a wide range of applications.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Roesser, "A discrete state-space model for linear image processing," *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 1–10, Feb. 1975, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TAC.1975.1100844>.
- [2] E. Fornasini and G. Marchesini, "State-space realization theory of two-dimensional filters," *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 484–492, Aug. 1976, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TAC.1976.1101305>.
- [3] E. Fornasini and G. Marchesini, "Doubly-indexed dynamical systems: State-space models and structural properties," *Mathematical systems theory*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 59–72, Dec. 1978, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01776566>.
- [4] J. Kurek, "The general state-space model for a two-dimensional linear digital system," *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 30, no. 6, pp. 600–602, Jun. 1985, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TAC.1985.1103998>.
- [5] N. Zerroug, K. Behih, Z. Bouchama, and K. Zehar, "Robust Adaptive Fuzzy Control of Nonlinear Systems," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 8328–8334, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4781>.
- [6] O. P. Bharti, R. K. Saket, and S. K. Nagar, "Controller Design For DFIG Driven By Variable Speed Wind Turbine Using Static Output Feedback Technique," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 1056–1061, Aug. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.697>.
- [7] D. Bakria, M. Azzouzi, and D. Gozim, "Chaos Control and Stabilization of a PID Controlled Buck Converter Using the Spotted Hyena Optimizer," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 7922–7926, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4585>.
- [8] G. Zames, "Feedback and optimal sensitivity: Model reference transformations, multiplicative seminorms, and approximate inverses," *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 26, no. 2, pp. 301–320, Apr. 1981, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TAC.1981.1102603>.
- [9] J. Doyle, K. Glover, P. Khargonekar, and B. Francis, "State-space solutions to standard H_2 and H_∞ control problems," in *1988 American Control Conference*, Atlanta, GA, USA, Jun. 1988, pp. 1691–1696, <https://doi.org/10.23919/ACC.1988.4789992>.
- [10] B. Hassibi, A. H. Sayed, and T. Kailath, *Indefinite-Quadratic Estimation and Control: A Unified Approach to H_2 and H_∞ Theories*. Philadelphia, PA, USA: SIAM, 1999.
- [11] B. A. Francis, *A course in H control theory*. Berlin, Germany: Springer-Verlag, 1987.
- [12] Z. Y. Feng, L. Xu, and Y. Anazawa, "Sufficient LMI conditions for H_∞ static output feedback control of 2-D systems," in *2010 11th International Conference on Control Automation Robotics & Vision*, Singapore, Sep. 2010, pp. 57–60, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICARCV.2010.5707419>.
- [13] C. K. Ahn, P. Shi, and M. V. Basin, "Two-Dimensional Dissipative Control and Filtering for Roesser Model," *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 60, no. 7, pp. 1745–1759, Jul. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TAC.2015.2398887>.
- [14] Z. Duan and Z. Xiang, "Output Feedback H_∞ Stabilization of 2-D Discrete Switched Systems in FM LSS Model," *Circuits, Systems, and Signal Processing*, vol. 33, no. 4, pp. 1095–1117, Apr. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00034-013-9680-6>.
- [15] H. Dong, Z. Wang, D. W. C. Ho, and H. Gao, "Robust H_∞ Fuzzy Output-Feedback Control With Multiple Probabilistic Delays and Multiple Missing Measurements," *IEEE Transactions on Fuzzy Systems*, vol. 18, no. 4, pp. 712–725, Dec. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TFUZZ.2010.2047648>.
- [16] Y. Zhao and Y. Qu, "The 36th Chinese Control Conference [Conference Reports]," *IEEE Control Systems Magazine*, vol. 38, no. 2, pp. 109–113, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MCS.2017.2786500>.
- [17] C. Du, L. Xie, and C. Zhang, " H_∞ control and robust stabilization of two-dimensional systems in Roesser models," *Automatica*, vol. 37, no. 2, pp. 205–211, Feb. 2001, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0005-1098\(00\)00155-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0005-1098(00)00155-2).
- [18] Z. Duan and Z. Xiang, " H_2 output feedback controller design for discrete-time 2-D switched systems," *Transactions of the Institute of Measurement and Control*, vol. 36, no. 1, pp. 68–77, Feb. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0142331213485279>.
- [19] Z.-Y. Feng and L. Xu, " H_∞ static output feedback controller design for two-dimensional discrete systems in Roesser model," in *2010 IEEE International Symposium on Computer-Aided Control System Design*, Yokohama, Japan, Sep. 2010, pp. 1790–1794, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CACSD.2010.5612799>.
- [20] Z. Y. Feng, L. Xu, M. Wu, and J.-H. She, " H_∞ Static Output Feedback Control of 2-D Discrete Systems in FM Second Model," *Asian Journal of Control*, vol. 14, no. 6, pp. 1505–1513, 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1002/asjc.472>.
- [21] L. Li, "Observer-based H_∞ controller for 2-D T-S fuzzy model," *International Journal of Systems Science*, vol. 47, no. 14, pp. 3455–3464, Oct. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207721.2015.1084396>.
- [22] L. Li, X. Li, and S. Ye, "Dynamic output feedback H_∞ control for 2-D fuzzy systems," *ISA Transactions*, vol. 95, pp. 1–10, Dec. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isatra.2018.12.029>.
- [23] Y. Luo, Z. Wang, J. Liang, G. Wei, and F. E. Alsaadi, " H_∞ Control for 2-D Fuzzy Systems With Interval Time-Varying Delays and Missing Measurements," *IEEE Transactions on Cybernetics*, vol. 47, no. 2, pp. 365–377, Oct. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCYB.2016.2514846>.
- [24] V. C. Pal and R. Negi, "Robust output feedback control of 2-D discrete systems with actuator saturation and time-varying delay," *Transactions of the Institute of Measurement and Control*, vol. 39, no. 11, pp. 1673–1695, Nov. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0142331216644045>.
- [25] D. Peng and X. Guan, "Output Feedback H_∞ Control for 2-D State-Delayed Systems," *Circuits, Systems & Signal Processing*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 147–167, Feb. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00034-008-9074-3>.
- [26] L. Xie, C. Du, Y. C. Soh, and C. Zhang, " H_∞ and Robust Control of 2-D Systems in FM Second Model," *Multidimensional Systems and Signal Processing*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 265–287, Jul. 2002, <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1015808429836>.
- [27] H. Xu, Y. Zou, S. Xu, and L. Guo, "Robust H_∞ Control for Uncertain Two-Dimensional Discrete Systems Described by the General Model via Output Feedback Controllers," *International Journal of Control, Automation, and Systems*, vol. 6, no. 5, pp. 785–791, Oct. 2008.
- [28] R. Yang, L. Xie, and C. Zhang, " H_2 and mixed H_2/H_∞ control of two-dimensional systems in Roesser model," *Automatica*, vol. 42, no. 9, pp. 1507–1514, Sep. 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.automatica.2006.04.002>.
- [29] K. Zhou, J. C. Doyle, and K. Glover, *Robust and optimal control*. Upper Saddle River, NJ, USA: Prentice Hall, 1996.
- [30] K. Glover and J. C. Doyle, "A state space approach to H_∞ optimal control," in *Three Decades of Mathematical System Theory: A Collection of Surveys at the Occasion of the 50th Birthday of Jan C.*

- Willems, H. Nijmeijer and J. M. Schumacher, Eds. Berlin, Germany: Springer, 1989, pp. 179–218.
- [31] B. Francis, J. Helton, and G. Zames, "H_∞-optimal feedback controllers for linear multivariable systems," *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 29, no. 10, pp. 888–900, Oct. 1984, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TAC.1984.1103387>.
- [32] C. Du, L. Xie, and Y. C. Soh, "H_∞ filtering of 2-D discrete systems," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 48, no. 6, pp. 1760–1768, Jun. 2000, <https://doi.org/10.1109/78.845933>.
- [33] C. Scherer, P. Gahinet, and M. Chilali, "Multiobjective output-feedback control via LMI optimization," *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 42, no. 7, pp. 896–911, Jul. 1997, <https://doi.org/10.1109/9.599969>.
- [34] P. Apkarian, P. Gahinet, and G. Becker, "Self-scheduled H_∞ control of linear parameter-varying systems: a design example," *Automatica*, vol. 31, no. 9, pp. 1251–1261, Sep. 1995, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0005-1098\(95\)00038-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0005-1098(95)00038-X).
- [35] E. I. L. Ghaoui, F. Oustry, and M. Ait Rami, "A cone complementarity linearization algorithms for static output feedback and related problems," *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 42, no. 8, pp. 1171–1176, 1997.
- [36] H. Xu, Y. Zou, S. Xu, and J. Lam, "Bounded real lemma and robust H_∞ control of 2-D singular Roesser models," *Systems & Control Letters*, vol. 54, no. 4, pp. 339–346, Apr. 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sysconle.2004.09.005>.
- [37] S. Kiririm and A. Hmamed, "Robust H_∞ filtering for uncertain 2-D singular systems with delays," in *2019 8th International Conference on Systems and Control (ICSC)*, Marrakesh, Morocco, Jul. 2019, pp. 88–93, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSC47195.2019.8950572>.
- [38] K. H. Lee, J. H. Lee, and W. H. Kwon, "Sufficient LMI conditions for H_∞ output feedback stabilization of linear discrete-time systems," *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 51, no. 4, pp. 675–680, Apr. 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TAC.2006.872766>.
- [39] H. Gao, Z. Wang, and C. Wang, "Improved H_∞ control of discrete-time fuzzy systems: a cone complementarity linearization approach," *Information Sciences*, vol. 175, no. 1, pp. 57–77, Sep. 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2004.10.004>.
- [40] P. Gahinet, A. Nemirovskii, A. J. Laub, and M. Chilali, "The LMI control toolbox," in *Proceedings of 1994 33rd IEEE Conference on Decision and Control*, Lake Buena Vista, FL, USA, Sep. 1994, vol. 3, pp. 2038–2041 vol.3, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CDC.1994.411440>.
- [41] S. Boyd, L. E. Ghaoui, E. Feron, and V. Balakrishnan, *Linear Matrix Inequalities in System and Control Theory*. Philadelphia, PA, USA: SIAM, 1994.
- [42] Z. Y. Feng, J. She, and L. Xu, "A brief review and insights into matrix inequalities for H_∞ static-output-feedback control and a local optimal solution," *International Journal of Systems Science*, vol. 50, no. 12, pp. 2292–2305, Sep. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207721.2019.1654008>.
- [43] Y. W. Wang, X.-K. Liu, J. W. Xiao, and Y. Shen, "Output formation-containment of interacted heterogeneous linear systems by distributed hybrid active control," *Automatica*, vol. 93, pp. 26–32, Jul. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.automatica.2018.03.020>.
- [44] J. K. Goyal, S. Ghosh, and S. Kamal, "New LMI conditions for H_∞/H₂ output feedback control of linear discrete-time systems," *International Journal of Control*, vol. 94, no. 6, pp. 1716–1722, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207179.2019.1665712>.
- [45] J. Chen, C. Lin, B. Chen, and Q. G. Wang, "Improved stability criterion and output feedback control for discrete time-delay systems," *Applied Mathematical Modelling*, vol. 52, pp. 82–93, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apm.2017.07.048>.
- [46] X.-H. Chang, R.-R. Liu, and J. H. Park, "A Further Study on Output Feedback H_{∞} Control for Discrete-Time Systems," *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems II: Express Briefs*, vol. 67, no. 2, pp. 305–309, Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCSII.2019.2904320>.
- [47] E. Pathan, A. A. Bakar, S. A. Zulkifi, M. H. Khan, H. Arshad, and M. Asad, "A Robust Frequency Controller based on Linear Matrix Inequality for a Parallel Islanded Microgrid," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 6264–6269, Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3769>.
- [48] O. Aydogdu and M. L. Levent, "Kalman State Estimation and LQR Assisted Adaptive Control Of a Variable Loaded Servo System," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 4125–4130, Jun. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2708>.
- [49] C. Lin, B. Chen, and Q.-G. Wang, "Static output feedback stabilization for fractional-order systems in T-S fuzzy models," *Neurocomputing*, vol. 218, pp. 354–358, Dec. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neucom.2016.08.085>.
- [50] R. Yang, S. Ding, and W. X. Zheng, "Co-design of event-triggered mechanism and dissipativity-based output feedback controller for two-dimensional systems," *Automatica*, vol. 130, Aug. 2021, Art. no. 109694, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.automatica.2021.109694>.
- [51] X. Lv, Y. Niu, and Z. Cao, "Sliding Mode Control for Uncertain 2-D FMII Systems Under Stochastic Scheduling," *IEEE Transactions on Cybernetics*, pp. 1–12, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCYB.2023.3267406>.

A Fairness-based Cell Selection Mechanism for Ultra-Dense Networks (UDNs)

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ABSTRACT

A typical 5G Ultra-Dense Network (UDN) comprises different types of Base Stations (BSs) in its structure. Dense deployment of small-cell BSs within a macrocell BS's coverage offers significant benefits, as the distance between a User Equipment (UE) and its small-cell BS is shorter with robust signals. Thus, the network capacity will increase dramatically. However, selecting an appropriate small-cell BS for a particular UE becomes a challenge in 5G UDNs. This study proposed a mechanism to address the cell selection problem and maximize fairness among UEs when making the cell selection decision. The proposed mechanism considered different parameters. The load balance for each small-cell BS was considered to fairly distribute UEs and avoid traffic congestion. Moreover, the signal strength was considered with the achievable data rate for all small-cell BSs to stimulate idle small-cell BSs to be in operating mode. A simulation was carried out in MATLAB to evaluate the proposed mechanism. Signal-to-Interference-Ratio (SINR) and Signal Strength (SS)-based strategies were also simulated for comparison. The proposed solution outperformed the other schemes in terms of fairness, as the UEs attached to the system were fairly distributed among small-cell BSs. Furthermore, the proposed mechanism achieved the best radio resource distribution in terms of fairness compared to the two other schemes.

Keywords-cell selection; UDN; small cells; fairness

I. INTRODUCTION

The fifth generation (5G) of wireless networks enables data to be shared and information to be accessed at any time, anywhere, and for any purpose [1]. Abundant new applications and service domains, such as smart transportation, smart cities, and the Internet of Things (IoT), must be supported by 5G technologies [2-3]. 5G provides high data rates, efficient use of energy, greater reliability, low latency, and extended coverage [4]. Technologies such as millimeter wave (mmWave) and Heterogeneous Ultra-Dense Networks (HUDN) are the most promising approaches to meet these requirements [5-6]. The density growth in current wireless cellular networks has brought some challenges that need to be resolved [7]. It is expected that the number of small cells installed will increase rapidly in the next few years [8]. An Ultra-Dense Network (UDN) is a network in which the number of active UEs is less than the number of small cells in the network [9]. UDNs have a high density of small cells, where the UE distribution would reach approximately 600 active users per kilometer [10]. Picocells and femtocells are examples of small low-power cells that make up HUDNs, while high-power legacy macrocells make up the majority of the network [4].

A typical UDN consists of various types of cells in its structure. Four distinct types of networks could be identified, depending on different coverage areas and application scenarios, as shown in Table I [11]:

- **Macrocell:** Typically, cellular networks use a macrocell architecture when a powerful BS serves a wide coverage area. The macrocell is always located in a high place, such as the apex of a mountain or a skyscraper. Therefore, it has a clear visibility of the surrounding environments and barriers, allowing for long transmission distances and wide coverage areas, with a cell radius that expands from 1 to 25 km. However, shadow fading and multipath interference have a significant impact on the Quality of Service (QoS) for UEs at cell edges. Additionally, the QoS for attached indoor UEs is affected when served by the macrocell, as a result of uneven service request distribution.
- **Microcell:** A microcell is served by a low-power BS in densely crowded urban areas. Its range is between 200 m and 1 km. This network is much more limited in scope than the much more widespread macrocell system. As the frequency reuse distance of low-power BS decreases, the number of channels and traffic density increase.
- **Picocell:** The coverage of a picocell network is less than the coverage of a microcell, as it ranges from 100 to 200 m. Indoor areas are frequently covered by picocells.
- **Femtocell:** A femtocell is a small, low-power BS designed to improve the quality of communications in residential or small business places. Compared to other cell types, femtocells are much easier to install and an efficient and cost-effective choice. Furthermore, femtocells could cover the gaps left by picocells and reduce signal loss.

TABLE I. TYPES OF UDN NETWORKS

Type	Transmission power (W)	Coverage
Macrocell	20-160	1 km -25 km
Microcell	2-20	300 m – 1 km
Picocell	0.25 - 2	100– 250 m
Femtocell	0.01 – 0.05	10 – 50m

The deployment of dense small-cell systems in existing macrocells offers significant benefits to traditional networks. With a short distance between a user and the BS, the level of signal strength will be robust and capacity will increase. Small cells can be deployed by end users, reducing the overall cost of deployment. Incoming network traffic can be balanced and offloaded over multiple cells. Small cells can be configured in a variety of ways to reduce interference and increase energy efficiency [12]. It is also possible to improve spectral efficiency by making efficient use of the spectrum and reusing frequencies over short distances [13-14]. However, HUDNs face difficulties such as transmission power management, radio resource allocation, cell selection, interference mitigation, and overhead signaling to coordinate among small cells [15].

The process of selecting adequate small cell BSs to provide services for a particular UE is recognized as the cell selection problem [16-17]. This is identified as an NP-hard optimization problem, and its computational complexity grows exponentially with the size of the network [18-19]. The effective and efficient use of a spectrum is a critical prerequisite for UDN 5G networks [20].

II. RELATED WORKS

Investigating cell selection involves multiple criteria, such as performance measurements and knowledge of mobility information. Information about mobility, such as the velocity and direction of the UEs, provides the foundation for many different applications. Most of the research focused on UEs with traveling vehicles. Instead, this study considered pedestrian UEs where their velocity does not have a critical impact on the cell selection decision. In [21] a topology-aware skipping technique was proposed, which analyzed the detrimental influence of UE speed on the achieved capacity in UDNs. This study was carried out to determine how to maximize network throughput. The location of the user and the size of the cell were taken into account when making a handover decision. The simulation results showed that the proposed scheme was more effective than the conventional one in terms of the average UE data rate. In [22], a cell selection technique for 5G UDNs was presented, employing a non-cooperative game theory with two players, one representing UE and the other representing BS. The simulation results showed that the proposed technique reduced the blockage rate experienced by users and increased the performance of 5G UDNs.

In [23], a cell selection method was proposed for 5G UDNs named Handover based on Resident Time Prediction (HO RTP). This scheme aimed to predict the amount of time spent inside a cell. Afterward, small-cell BS was selected considering two facts: First, the small-cell BS with the highest RSSI value was considered, and second, a resident duration that is longer than a predefined threshold value was considered for selection.

In terms of achievable mean user throughput, the simulation results showed that this method was better than the traditional one. In [24], Adaptive Cell Selection (ADA-CS) was proposed for 5G UDNs, choosing the optimal BS by considering various characteristics of UDNs and vehicular motions. The proposed scheme consisted of six steps: configuration, decision-making, filtering, narrowing, selecting, and HO triggering. The simulation showed that the ADA-CS method outperformed the conventional and current related approaches in terms of the median number of handovers, the median feasible downlink data rates, and the median spectral efficiency.

In [25], the Q-learning algorithm was presented for the cell selection problem, supporting UEs to select their appropriate BS autonomously. UEs could learn to attain equilibrium without centralized control for collecting information from other UEs. The simulation results demonstrated the convergence of the proposed algorithm and its efficiency. A novel strategy for the cell selection problem was presented in [26]. This method classified all cells into distinct groups based on priority levels. Then, the cell with the highest priority degree would be selected. As a result, the probability of triggering a cell selection decision was reduced. The problem of cell selection was discussed in [27]. The proposed scheme presented two Hidden Markov Model (HMM)-based Machine Learning (ML) algorithms. The proposed HMM-based ML systems had multiple goals, and the main goal was to improve the dependability and availability of network resources. The simulation results demonstrated that the proposed strategy could overcome the random cell selection method in terms of channel availability and dependability. A flexible and hard cell selection method was proposed for non-uniform HetNets in [28], considering the position of the UE. The positions were classified into three categories: inner region, annular region, and outer region. The hard cell selection decision was used in both the inner and outer regions, but the flexible cell selection decision was used in the annular region. The results of the analysis showed that both the coverage and user throughput improved greatly. In [29], Movement-Aware Coordinated multipoint Handover (MACH) and improved MACH (iMACH) were proposed to manage handover and cell selection issues in 5G UDNs. The MACH approach considered the UE's stay time at a specific cell BS. The iMACH approach considered two factors: dwell time and nearest BSs. The simulation results showed that the proposed strategies could overcome the compared ones in terms of handover probability minimization, coverage probability, and throughput increases.

In [18], a deep learning cell selection strategy was suggested, representing the challenge of user association as a segmentation issue in an image, based on pixel-scale categorization. A traditional U-Net network model was built to perform the cell selection task while complying with the requirements of load balancing and UE fairness. The suggested U-Net model took the channel gain matrix as input and considered factors such as path loss, shadowing, and gain. The BS-associated matrix would be determined according to the trained model when it was demodulated. The network was designed as a two-tier UDN, including two macro-BSs and eight small BSs. The BSs were randomly dispersed within a region measuring 600 m on each side. The simulation results

showed that the UDN-based deep learning approach surpassed the asymptotically optimum Genetic Algorithm (GA) in terms of the time needed for computation and the degree to scale with the size of the network. A mobility-aware cell selection method for mmWave networks was introduced in [30], considering the distribution of loads in small cells to prevent cell congestion. This method addressed issues of non-line-of-sight propagation effects, blocking, and directionless while decreasing the frequency of handovers between small-cell BSs. In addition, it could accommodate changes in network topology and channel conditions. In [31], the QoS of high-speed mobility in LTE was discussed, measuring handover performance while UEs moved at high speed. The results were classified into multiple classes according to UE speed, showing that it could be determined when handover could fail and the call could be dropped.

The limitations of the recent cell selection methods can be summarized as follows:

- Fairness issues have not been studied in depth in recent cell selection strategies. The issue of UE fairness must be considered when making the cell selection decision. Fair distribution of radio resources among UEs is also necessary to maintain user satisfaction.
- Most contemporary studies give the highest priority to cells that have the strongest reception power to maximize the amount of data rate.
- The issue of starvation, which can be faced by distributed UEs, has not been considered in most current studies. Starvation occurs when more UEs are congested in a single small-cell BS, where the radio resources of a small-cell BS are limited and might not satisfy UE requests.
- Most studies used static and nonadaptive methods when making the cell selection decision. Since HetNets have several tiers, adaptive selection is preferable.
- Most strategies have focused on selecting an adequate cell for a high-speed moving vehicle. However, small-cell BSs can be deployed in areas that have pedestrian UEs, where the handover decision might not be necessary because the UEs are stationary or move very slowly.

This study aims to:

- Propose an adaptive cell selection mechanism to maximize fairness among UEs. The proposed scheme aimed to map UEs to adequate small-cell BSs under the fairness constraint, considering load balance, signal strength, Signal-to-Interference-Ratio (SINR), and achievable throughput.
- Evaluate the proposed mechanism in a 5G UDN model, simulating a real-time environment.
- Conduct a MATLAB simulation to evaluate the proposed mechanism, using different performance metrics, such as data rate and fairness, to investigate its feasibility. The average throughput of the whole system was also considered. Furthermore, Jain's fairness index was used to evaluate the achievable fairness of the proposed mechanism. The process of distributing UEs among small-

cell BSs, which depends on the cell selection decision, was evaluated in terms of fairness, and the fairness of distributing radio resources among UEs was investigated.

III. SYSTEM MODEL

A 5G UDN was considered, consisting of small high-density 5G cells, deployed within the range of a single macrocell. Small cells operated with different subbands of the available spectrum to avoid and mitigate interference. The division of the available spectrum was performed based on the method proposed in [32]. The small BSs operated on a carrier frequency of 28 GHz with a bandwidth of 500 MHz. The available bandwidth N consisted of multiple subchannels, where $N=[n_1, n_2, n_3, \dots, n_n]$. Small cells were randomly distributed within the macrocell area. X and Y were the coordinates of the macro-BS. The distribution of the small BSs depends on those coordinates, as their locations would be maintained to not be placed out of the macrocell's range. The set S comprises all BSs of small cells in the system $S=[s_1, s_2, s_3, \dots, s_n]$. Additionally, UEs were distributed randomly. The system would insert a new UE for each run and apply the cell selection strategy. The set U comprises all UEs that request resources in terms of downlink, where $U_i=[UE_1, UE_2, UE_3, \dots, UE_n]$. Location information for all small BSs, UE, and macrocell is necessary to calculate the distance between UEs and their serving small BSs, and the between UEs and other small BSs. This information was used to calculate the necessary propagation models, such as path loss.

It was assumed that $T_{x_s,UE,n}$ indicates the transmission power for a specific sub-channel n_i for a particular UE UE_i , which is associated with a small cell BS s_i . The transmission power dedication matrix of a particular s_i small cell BS is denoted by $T_x=[T_{x_s,UE,n}]_{s \times UE \times n}$. The sub-channel scheduling indicator matrix is denoted by $CH=[ch_{s,UE,n}]_{s \times UE \times n}$. If the subchannel n_i would be allocated to a UE UE_j in small-cell BS s_k , $CH_{s,UE,n}$ otherwise $CH_{s,UE,n}=0$. The capacity of subchannel n , which is assigned for UE by a small cell BS s , is calculated as follows [33]:

$$C_{s,UE,n} = \Delta f \log_2(1 + \alpha \text{SINR}_{s,UE,n}) \quad (1)$$

where Δf and α indicate the subcarrier spacing and the target BER set to 10^{-6} , respectively. The SINR would be calculated according to the following formula [33]:

$$\text{SINR}_{UE,n} = \frac{T_{x_s,n} G_{s,UE,n}}{\sum_{MBS} T_{x_{MBS,n}} G_{MBS,UE,n} + \sum_{s'} T_{x_{s'},n} G_{s',UE,n} + N_0 \Delta f} \quad (2)$$

where $T_{x_s,n}$ represents the transmission power of the serving small cell BS s on sub-channel n , $G_{s,UE,n}$ indicates the channel gain between the serving small cell BS s and its UE on subchannel n , $T_{x_{MBS,n}}$ indicates the transmission power of macrocell BS MBS on subchannel n , $G_{MBS,UE,n}$ indicates the channel gain between MBS and UE on subchannel n , $T_{x_{s'},n}$ indicates the transmission power of the adjacent small cell BS s' on subchannel n , $G_{s',UE,n}$ indicates the channel gain between adjacent small cell BS s' and UE on sub-channel n . The channel gain is calculated as follows [33]:

$$G = 10^{-PL/10} \quad (3)$$

where PL is the path loss calculated based on two considerations: First when the small cell BS is installed indoors and its associated UEs are in the same environment. In this case, it is calculated according to [33]:

$$PL_{indb} = 38.46 + 20\log_{10}(D) + 0.7d_{2R,in} + 18.3^{((n+2)/(n+1)-0.46)} + V_x * L_{inwall} \quad (4)$$

where D is the distance in meters, $0.7d_{2R,in}$ is the penetration loss caused by the walls inside buildings, the floors are accounted as n , V indicates the total number of walls between the small cell BS and its attached UEs, and L_{inwall} is the penetration loss caused by walls that separate adjacent buildings. The second consideration assumed that small-cell BS is installed in an indoor environment and its associated UEs are positioned outdoors. In this case, the path loss would be calculated according to [33]:

$$PL_{indb} = \max(15.3 + 37.6 \log_{10}(D), 38.4 + 20\log_{10}(D)) + 0.7d_{2R,in} + \sqrt{18.3n^{((n+2)/(n+1)-0.46)} + V_x * L_{inwall} + L_{outwall}} \quad (5)$$

IV. PROPOSED SOLUTION

Usually, UEs periodically scan and inspect the received signals from all adjacent small-cell BSs. Additionally, all small-cell BSs would be aware of the number of attached UEs. Moreover, the information about the achievable data rates for each UE attached to a particular small-cell BS is known by the serving small-cell BSs. In addition, SINR information is also known for small-cell BSs. All of this information can be used to design a novel strategy for cell selection in which UEs are attached to a proper small-cell BS. The proposed solution was designed to improve the cell selection decision using the aforementioned information and assist small-cell BSs to serve their attached UEs appropriately. The proposed scheme aims to improve spectrum utilization and fairness among UEs. Fairness includes the fairness of radio resource distribution among UEs and the fairness of UEs distribution among small-cell BSs. Accordingly, information about load balance for each small-cell BS, the achievable data rate for each UE, Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI), and SINR were used to form the proposed solution.

A. Load Balance

The load balance that considers the number of UEs assigned for each small-cell BS needs to be configured in the proposed solution. In addition, an indication of the utilization of all resources in UDN would be known and used during the cell selection decision process. In this context, load balance consists of both the total number of UEs in each small-cell BS and the total number of UEs served represented as u . Moreover, the total number of UEs in a particular small cell BS is represented as u_{s_i} . Those two facts are needed to determine both α_{s_i} and β_{s_i} , which are calculated as follows:

$$\alpha_{s_i} = \frac{u_{s_i}}{u} \quad (6)$$

Every small cell BS s_i has a predefined target τ for the total number of UEs that would be served, which is used to calculate β_{s_i} as follows:

$$\beta_{s_i} = \frac{u_{s_i}}{\tau} \quad (7)$$

where the range of τ is maintained as follows:

$$4 < \tau < 12 \quad (8)$$

B. Channel Condition

The second step of the proposed strategy was to evaluate the channel condition between distributed small-cell BSs and their UEs. SINR provides knowledge about the channel condition between the UE and small-cell BS s_i in terms of interference. This knowledge is necessary for the proposed strategy when making the cell selection decision. Equation (2) describes the SINR formula. Another significant factor to inspect the channel condition is RSSI, which represents the strength of the received signal. However, RSSI discards the interference temperature, which would be propagated by neighboring small-cell BSs. Thus, the aforementioned factors are used in the second step according to the following:

$$\gamma_{s_i,ue_j} = \frac{SINR_{s_i,ue_j}}{\delta} \quad (9)$$

where δ represents the target SINR, which is predefined as a target interference avoidance value in the system, and ue_j indicates the newly inserted UE. Accordingly, the channel condition indicator in this system is calculated by:

$$\varepsilon_{s_i,ue_j} = (\gamma_{s_i,ue_j} \times RSSI_{s_i,ue_j}) \quad (10)$$

C. Achievable Data Rate

The third step of the proposed strategy is to investigate the achievable data rate for every small-cell BS. Knowledge about the achievable data rate would be key to supporting fairness among UEs. In this system, idle small-cell BS might also be stimulated to operate and accept UEs. From (1), the average data rate for a group of UEs attached to a particular small-cell BS s_i can be extracted. Consequently, the average data rate can be configured as follows:

$$\zeta_{s_i} = \frac{\sum_{ue=1}^n C_{s_i,UE}}{u_{s_i}} \quad (11)$$

Afterward, the average data rate for all installed small cell BSs in the system would be considered. In this case, the idle small cell BS would influence the decision of selecting a target BS when a new UE requests resources. The following formula provides the average small cell BSs' capacity:

$$\theta = \frac{\sum_{s=1}^k \zeta_s}{s} \quad (12)$$

where S is the number of small cell BSs in the system. This equation is used to realize the proportional utilization of the distributed small cell BSs. The result shows whether distributed small-cell BSs are fully used or if there are idle small-cell BSs. Thus, the cell selection decision would be affected by the result of the following formula:

$$\lambda = \frac{\theta}{\psi} \quad (13)$$

where ψ is the target average capacity for all small cell BSs in the system. In this target, all small cell BSs are operated with all available resources under good channel conditions.

D. UE and Small Cell BS Match Table

In the last step, every small cell BS would be aware of the variable value of its function computed according to (14). This formula measures the current load balance for each small-cell BS, the channel condition between the small-cell BS and the candidate UE, and the data rate of distributed UEs and their serving small-cell BSs:

$$\psi_{s_i,ue_j} = \frac{(\beta_{s_i} \times \lambda)}{(\alpha_{s_i} \times \epsilon_{s_i,ue_j})} \tag{14}$$

This equation depends directly on (6), (7), (10), and (13). The parameters β_{s_i} and α_{s_i} are used to balance the expression output. Table II shows the match between a newly inserted UE and all small-cell BSs based on (14). Accordingly, the small cell BS s_i with the highest value will be assigned for the new user ue_j . However, if the small cell BS s_i that has the highest value reaches the predefined target number of UEs τ , the new UE ue_j will not be assigned for this matched small-cell BS s_i . Instead, it will be assigned to a small-cell BS s_x , which has the next highest value of the function in (14). The pseudo-code for the proposed mechanism is illustrated in Algorithm 1.

TABLE II. UE/SMALL CELL BS MATCH TABLE

UE	s_1	s_2	s_3	s_i
ue_j	ψ_{s_1,ue_j}	ψ_{s_2,ue_j}	ψ_{s_3,ue_j}	ψ_{s_i,ue_j}

Algorithm 1 Proposed Mechanism

Inputs $\leftarrow S, u, u_{s_i}, \psi, \delta, \tau$

FOR $i = 1$ to S do

 compute α_{s_i}

 compute β_{s_i}

 FOR $j = 1$ to ue_{s_i} do

 capacity $_{s_i,ue_j}$

 End FOR

 compute ζ_{s_i}

θ, λ

 compute: ψ_{s_i,ue_j}

END FOR

V. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A simulation was carried out in MATLAB to evaluate the performance of the proposed method on a 5G UDN, comprised of high-density 5G small-cell BSs. A single macrocell BS was implemented with randomly distributed small-cell BSs within its coverage, considering the concept of a two-tier network. Accordingly, small cells shared different subbands from the available spectrum to alleviate interference. The division of the available spectrum was performed based on the method proposed in [32]. The small cell BSs operate on a carrier frequency of 28 GHz with a bandwidth of 500 MHz. The available bandwidth N consists of multiple subchannels, where $N=[n_1, n_2, n_3, \dots, n_n]$.

The Orthogonal Frequency-Division Multiple Access (OFDMA) transmission method was adopted, and multiple subcarriers formed the frequency band. A particular Resource Block (RB) was constructed from 12 adjacent subcarriers. RB is a basic unit that can be allocated to a particular user. The

UEs were distributed randomly within the macrocell BS coverage. The number of UEs served should not exceed the predefined target. Path loss, SINR, and noise influence on channel gain between any UE and its serving small-cell BS were considered. Thus, the channel condition varies from one UE to another. Table III presents the simulation parameters.

TABLE III. SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
Number of small cell BSs S	40
Number of Distributed UEs u	200
Small cell BS Transmission Power	30 dBm
Macrocell BS Transmission Power	46 dBm
Carrier Frequency	28 GHz
Bandwidth	500 MHz
Small Cell BS Radius	25 m – 100 m
White Noise Power Density	174 dBm/Hz
Carrier Spacing	15 kHz

The performance of the system was evaluated in terms of average throughput and fairness among the distributed UEs. The proposed scheme was compared with two other schemes. The SINR-based scheme directed the cell selection decision toward interference mitigation since UE was assigned to its small-cell BS according to SINR. In this case, the channel condition and interference were both considered when making the cell selection decision. The other scheme was the Signal Strength (SS)-based scheme, where the cell selection decision was made according to the strength of the received signal. Thus, a particular UE would be assigned to the small-cell BS having the strongest received signal regardless of interference.

Fig. 1. Small cell network average throughput.

Figure 1 shows the average throughput of the whole network during the cell selection decision for different strategies. The three schemes were evaluated by increasing the number of UEs. The SS-based scheme outperformed the other two schemes because the cell selection decision was made with the best channel condition. Signal strength influences the quality of the received data, and thus the data rate increases. However, in this case, some of the small-cell BSs might be unused or have less number of associated UEs. As a result, this will impact the full utilization of the available resources. The average throughput would decrease as more UEs are inserted

into the system. The SINR-based scheme had the worst average throughput. The cell selection decision for the SINR-based scheme was made according to the SINR value received for each UE. Then, the cell selection decision would be made to match the small-cell BS with the best received SINR value with the UE. The channel condition was used to alleviate the undesired impact of interference, but this will affect the capacity of the network. Average throughput decreased as the number of UEs increased. In contrast, the average throughput of the proposed scheme was between the SINR- and SS-based schemes, as the proposed scheme does not only tend only adopt the strength of the signal or to only focus on alleviating the interference. Instead, the proposed scheme acknowledges both factors by considering both signal strength and interference mitigation. In addition, the load balance for all small-cell BSs was considered. Finally, the average throughput of all three schemes decreased as the number of UEs increased. This became obvious after inserting 40 UEs into the system.

The Jain fairness index was used to evaluate the fairness among the distributed UEs. Figure 2 shows the fairness among the UEs for all three schemes. The proposed scheme exhibited the best fairness index result compared to the others. Fairness in this context was derived from the achievable throughput for all UEs in the system. According to Figure 2, the results of the fairness index can be distinguished when more UEs are inserted into the network. Achieving fairness among UEs is applicable with fewer and a limited number of UEs. However, the fairness results were not precise because the number of UEs was limited and there were no distinguished differences for achievable throughput of the limited number of UEs. When the number of UEs increased, especially over 100, the proposed scheme outperformed the SINR-based and SS-based schemes. The proposed scheme considered the load balance, channel condition, and achievable throughput. Thus, the cell selection decision attempted to increase capacity under a fairness constraint. On the contrary, the fairness index results showed lower fairness among UEs for both SINR-based and SS-based schemes.

Fig. 2. Fairness index.

Figure 3 shows the fairness distribution of radio resources among UEs, depicting the radio resource allocation for the UEs distributed in the system. The SS-based scheme achieved the worst fairness distribution of radio resources compared to the proposed and SINR-based schemes. This is because the SS-based scheme assigns UEs to the small-cell BS that has the strongest signal. In this case, the load balance and the number of UEs attached to a particular small-cell BS would not be recognized. Consequently, over-limited UEs will share the radio resources of a single small-cell BS, reducing the allocated portion of radio resources for each attached UE. This fairness index result decreased as the number of UEs inserted increased. In contrast, the proposed scheme achieved the best result in the fair distribution of radio resources. Moreover, fairness increased when the number of attached UEs increased due to consideration of the load balance for small-cell BSs and the definition of a target threshold number of UEs for each small-cell BS. The result of the fairness index became more obvious when the number of attached UEs increased. Additionally, the fairness result of the SINR-based scheme for the distribution of radio resources was worse than that of the proposed scheme.

Fig. 3. Radio resources distribution among served UEs.

The process of mapping UEs for their appropriate small cell BS depends on the cell selection mechanism. Figures 4-7 present the distribution of UEs among small-cell BSs. Figure 4 shows the fairness index for distributing UEs and selecting their serving small-cell BSs for all three schemes. The proposed scheme showed the best fair distribution of UEs compared to the other two schemes, achieving a fairness index of 0.9. This was because the decision on cell selection was made considering parameters, such as load balance, received signal strength, and SINR. If load balance was considered in the cell selection decision, the UEs would be evenly distributed among small-cell BSs. Moreover, an idle small-cell BS will have an opportunity to operate, and thus the utilization of the available resources will be improved. Additionally, there should be a target threshold, which should not be exceeded, for the number of UEs that small-cell BS would accept to serve. This threshold depends on different factors, such as the available spectrum, the number of small-cell BSs serving, and the expected number of future attached UEs. When UEs are distributed fairly among small-cell BSs, each UE would have the same portion of the shared spectrum. In contrast, the SINR-based scheme achieved the lowest degree of fairness and the SS-based scheme gained a moderate degree of fairness. This can influence the random distribution of UEs across the grid and shows that UEs are randomly distributed throughout macrocell coverage.

Fig. 4. UE distribution fairness index.

In addition, the cell selection strategy reflects the case of UE distribution among all small-cell BSs in the system. UE distribution varies according to the adopted cell selection strategy. The coverage of the macrocell was divided into four subregions, obeying the following strategy: a center cell subregion and three outer subregions. Consequently, small-cell BSs were distributed and implemented in different subregions. Accordingly, all small-cell BSs positioned in the same subregion were grouped in one cluster. Thus, cluster one represents small-cell BSs positioned in the center subregion. The other clusters, clusters 2, 3, and 4, represent small-cell BSs positioned in the outer subregions.

Figure 5 represents the UE distribution among small-cell BSs with their clusters for the SINR-based scheme. According to Figure 5, the SINR-based scheme never assigns UEs for small-cell BSs positioned in the center subregion (cluster 1). This is because all small-cell BSs in the center subregion experience a high temperature of undesirable interference. The main source of interference is the macrocell BS because it is very close to this subregion. Thus, all UEs were assigned to small-cell BSs in the outer subregions. This explains why UE distribution among small-cell BSs gained a worse fairness degree for this scheme compared to the other two. For example, the average of distributing 200 UEs among four clusters would be 50, while it was 30 according to Figure 5. The gap is obvious in this case where cluster 1 had zero UE and clusters 2 and 3 had 80 UEs. Figure 6 shows the UE distribution across all four clusters for the SS-based scheme, showing a nearly fair UE distribution when the number of UEs is less than 50. However, the gap between the number of UEs assigned for each cluster expanded when the number of UEs increased to over 50. For example, the gap reaches 50 when the number of UEs becomes 150. In this case, 80 UEs were assigned only for small-cell BSs located in the center subregion, while 70 UEs were distributed among the three other subregions. When the number of UEs became 200, this gap became huge. In this situation, only 20 UEs were assigned for small-cell BSs positioned in cluster 3, while 80 were assigned to small-cell BSs in cluster 1. Consequently, the gap between 80 and 20 is still unfavorable.

Fig. 5. UE distribution for the SINR-based scheme.

Fig. 6. UE distribution for the SS-based scheme.

Fig. 7. UE distribution for the proposed scheme.

Figure 7 shows the UE distribution across the different clusters for the proposed scheme. According to Figure 7, the gap decreased as the number of UEs inserted increased. This became clearer when the number of UEs was 150 or 200. When the number of UEs was 150, the gap shrank between 10-20. Also, when the number of UEs reached 200, the gap degree resided approximately between 20-30. This gives an advantage in limiting the served UEs with a predefined target threshold and sheds light on the necessity of considering the load balance for each small-cell BS to allow fair distribution of UEs among serving small-cell BSs. Additionally, including load balance in cell selection decisions would support fairness among served UEs, as it would attempt to preserve as much network capacity as possible. Moreover, the spectral efficiency would also be enhanced.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study investigated the cell selection problem in a 5G UDN environment. A typical UDN consists of different cell types in its structure: macrocell, microcell, picocell, and femtocell. The deployment of dense small-cell BSs within the extent of a macrocell BS provides significant benefits. The distance between a serviced UE and its mapped small-cell BS is short. This will increase the capacity of the network because the received signal would be in good condition. However, UDNs face challenges, such as the cell selection problem. The basic process of cell selection decision is to map UEs with their appropriate small-cell BS based on predefined parameters and strategies. This study proposed a mechanism to address the cell selection problem, intending to maximize fairness among UEs when making the cell selection decision. The proposed mechanism considers different parameters and aspects. The load balance of each small-cell BS was considered to fairly distribute UEs among small-cell BSs. In addition, it was used to avoid congestion for a particular small-cell BS. Signal strength was also considered and the achievable data rate for all small-cell BSs was investigated and analyzed to stimulate an idle small-cell BS to be in operating mode. All these factors were considered when the cell selection decision was made for the proposed mechanism. A simulation was performed in MATLAB to evaluate the proposed mechanism, incorporating both the SINR-based and SS-based schemes for comparison. The proposed solution outperformed the other two schemes in terms of fairness, and the attached UEs were fairly distributed among small-cell BSs. Moreover, the proposed mechanism achieved the best radio resource distribution in terms of fairness. In future work, handover and mobility issues would be further studied and incorporated into this scheme.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Lei, G. Zhu, C. Shen, Y. Xu, and X. Zhang, "Delay-Aware User Association and Power Control for 5G Heterogeneous Network," *Mobile Networks and Applications*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 491–503, Apr. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11036-018-1152-6>.
- [2] Y. Djeldjeli and M. Zoubir, "CP-SDN: A New Approach for the Control Operation of 5G Mobile Networks to Improve QoS," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 6857–6863, Apr. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4016>.
- [3] Z. A. Shamsan, "Statistical Analysis of 5G Channel Propagation using MIMO and Massive MIMO Technologies," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7417–7423, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4264>.
- [4] B. U. Kazi and G. A. Wainer, "Next generation wireless cellular networks: ultra-dense multi-tier and multi-cell cooperation perspective," *Wireless Networks*, vol. 25, no. 4, pp. 2041–2064, May 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11276-018-1796-y>.
- [5] A. Shabbir, H. R. Khan, S. A. Ali, and S. Rizvi, "Design and Performance Analysis of Multi-tier Heterogeneous Network through Coverage, Throughput and Energy Efficiency," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 2345–2350, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1256>.
- [6] M. Azhar and A. Shabbir, "5G Networks: Challenges and Techniques for Energy Efficiency," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 2864–2868, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1623>.
- [7] J. Zhao, Y. Liu, Y. Gong, C. Wang, and L. Fan, "A Dual-Link Soft Handover Scheme for C/U Plane Split Network in High-Speed Railway," *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 12473–12482, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2794770>.
- [8] W.-S. Kim, G. J. V. Lieshout, S.-H. Kim, and S.-B. Kim, "Method and apparatus for reporting buffer state by user equipment in communication system," U.S. Patent 10708940B2, Jul. 07, 2020.
- [9] A. Gotsis, S. Stefanatos, and A. Alexiou, "UltraDense Networks: The New Wireless Frontier for Enabling 5G Access," *IEEE Vehicular Technology Magazine*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 71–78, Jun. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MVT.2015.2464831>.
- [10] Y. Wei and S.-H. Hwang, "Optimization of Cell Size in Ultra-Dense Networks with Multiattribute User Types and Different Frequency Bands," *Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing*, vol. 2018, Oct. 2018, Art. no. e8319749, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/8319749>.
- [11] S. Alotaibi, "HetNet Characteristics and Models in 5G Networks," *International Journal of Computer Science & Network Security*, vol. 22, no. 4, pp. 27–32, 2022.
- [12] A. Mesodiakaki, E. Zola, and A. Kassler, "User association in 5G heterogeneous networks with mesh millimeter wave backhaul links," in *2017 IEEE 18th International Symposium on A World of Wireless, Mobile and Multimedia Networks (WoWMoM)*, Macau, China, Jun. 2017, pp. 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1109/WoWMoM.2017.7974342>.
- [13] Z. Qin, X. Yue, Y. Liu, Z. Ding, and A. Nallanathan, "User Association and Resource Allocation in Unified NOMA Enabled Heterogeneous Ultra Dense Networks," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 56, no. 6, pp. 86–92, Jun. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MCOM.2018.1700497>.
- [14] X. Wang, Y. Xu, J. Wang, and S. Fu, "Joint User Association and Power Allocation in Heterogeneous NOMA Networks With Imperfect CSI," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 47607–47618, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2979491>.
- [15] M. Tayyab, G. P. Koudouridis, X. Gelabert, and R. Jäntti, "Uplink Reference Signals for Energy-Efficient Handover," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 163060–163076, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3020618>.
- [16] A. Zakeri, A. Khalili, M. R. Javan, N. Mokari, and E. Jorswieck, "Robust Energy-Efficient Resource Management, SIC Ordering, and Beamforming Design for MC MISO-NOMA Enabled 6G," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 69, pp. 2481–2498, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSP.2021.3068362>.
- [17] A. Jahid, A. B. Shams, and M. F. Hossain, "PV-Powered CoMP-Based Green Cellular Networks with a Standby Grid Supply," *International Journal of Photoenergy*, vol. 2017, Apr. 2017, Art. no. e6189468, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/6189468>.
- [18] Y. Zhang, L. Xiong, and J. Yu, "Deep Learning Based User Association in Heterogeneous Wireless Networks," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 197439–197447, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3033133>.
- [19] J. G. Andrews, S. Singh, Q. Ye, X. Lin, and H. S. Dhillon, "An overview of load balancing in hetnets: old myths and open problems," *IEEE Wireless Communications*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 18–25, Apr. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MWC.2014.6812287>.
- [20] N. Javaid, A. Sher, H. Nasir, and N. Guizani, "Intelligence in IoT-Based 5G Networks: Opportunities and Challenges," *IEEE Communications*

- Magazine, vol. 56, no. 10, pp. 94–100, Oct. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MCOM.2018.1800036>.
- [21] R. Arshad, H. Elsayy, S. Sorour, T. Y. Al-Naffouri, and M.-S. Alouini, "Handover Management in 5G and Beyond: A Topology Aware Skipping Approach," *IEEE Access*, vol. 4, pp. 9073–9081, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2016.2642538>.
- [22] M. Gharam and N. Boudriga, "Cell Selection Game in 5G Heterogeneous Networks," in *Ubiquitous Networking*, Hammamet, Tunisia, 2018, pp. 28–39, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-02849-7_3.
- [23] Z. Qin, W. Feng, Z. Yue, and H. Tian, "A Handover Management Strategy Using Residence Time Prediction in 5G Ultra-Dense Networks," in *Signal and Information Processing, Networking and Computers*, Singapore, 2021, pp. 808–816, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-33-4102-9_97.
- [24] I. A. Alablani and M. A. Arafah, "An Adaptive Cell Selection Scheme for 5G Heterogeneous Ultra-Dense Networks," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 64224–64240, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3075324>.
- [25] X. Tan, X. Luan, Y. Cheng, A. Liu, and J. Wu, "Cell selection in two-tier femtocell networks using Q-learning algorithm," in *16th International Conference on Advanced Communication Technology*, Pyeongchang, Korea (South), Oct. 2014, pp. 1031–1035, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICACT.2014.6779115>.
- [26] L. Wang, W. Huang, Y. Fan, and X. Wang, "Priority-based cell selection for mobile equipments in heterogeneous cloud radio access networks," in *2015 International Conference on Connected Vehicles and Expo (ICCVE)*, Shenzhen, China, Jul. 2015, pp. 62–67, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCVE.2015.53>.
- [27] I. A. M. Balapuwaduge and F. Y. Li, "Hidden Markov Model Based Machine Learning for mMTC Device Cell Association in 5G Networks," in *ICC 2019 - 2019 IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC)*, Shanghai, China, Feb. 2019, pp. 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICC.2019.8761913>.
- [28] B. R. Alyaei, I. M. Qureshi, S. Saleem, and S. H. Abbassi, "Offloading With Hybrid Cell Association in Non-Uniform Heterogeneous Cellular Networks: Modeling and Performance Analysis," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 172214–172230, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2955934>.
- [29] W. Sun, L. Wang, J. Liu, N. Kato, and Y. Zhang, "Movement Aware CoMP Handover in Heterogeneous Ultra-Dense Networks," *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, vol. 69, no. 1, pp. 340–352, Jan. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCOMM.2020.3019388>.
- [30] A. S. Cacciapuoti, "Mobility-Aware User Association for 5G mmWave Networks," *IEEE Access*, vol. 5, pp. 21497–21507, 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2017.2751422>.
- [31] A. a. M. K. Abuelgasim and K. M. Yusof, "High Speed Mobility Management Performance in a Real LTE Scenario," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 5175–5179, Feb. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3245>.
- [32] S. Alotaibi and H. Sinky, "Power and Radio Resource Management in Femtocell Networks for Interference Mitigation," *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 14, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 4843, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s21144843>.
- [33] "Study on channel model for frequencies from 0.5 to 100 GHz," 3GPP, Sophia Antipolis, France, Technical Report 38.901, May 2017.

Computational Fluid Dynamics Evaluation of an Oil-flooded Screw Compressor

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ABSTRACT

The cost of energy is directly influenced by geopolitical, economic, and environmental factors. There is an international trend towards renewable resources, although the implementation pace and legislation in force have issues. Complete abolishment of fossil fuels is practically impossible. Evolution is only possible with the use of these fuels but with modern, efficient equipment to reduce the pollution resulting from the process of extracting, processing, and using fossil fuels. In this paper, a screw compressor with oil injection, used in oil extraction stations, is analyzed numerically. This analysis is useful in the process of modernizing and improving the efficiency of this type of compressor, which is capable of operating in extreme working regimes, highly contaminated with impurities. The numerical analysis presented certain challenges related to biphasic flow in extremely small spaces at high compression ratios. The results include the absolute pressure variation and the flow rate variation. Regarding future research, test series will be carried out to validate the numerical results on the test bench with a 1:1 scale prototype.

Keywords-screw compressor; multiphase flow; CFD; volumetric efficiency

I. INTRODUCTION

Screw compressors are compact, volumetric rotary devices with a few moving parts that function efficiently over a wide range of speeds and pressures [1]. Their application in many areas is relatively new. Compressors with two rotors ("male" and "female," or leading rotor and driven rotor) were invented in 1955 [2], while single-rotor compressors were presented in 1971 [3]. As a result, there are only a few providers globally, and INCDT COMOTI is the sole unit in Romania that investigates and produces such equipment [4]. The volume index (V_i) and the form of the rotors are the two most important structural components on which the compression process is dependent. The rotor geometry of the most popular screw compressors is based on the Sveridge Rotor Maskiner (SRM) license, with a "male" rotor with four lobes and a "female" rotor with six channels [5]. These compressors' flow rate is governed by the rotor diameter and length, as well as speed. After the '80s, the profiles known as Sigma were created, resulting in rotor diameters as small as 100 mm and speeds as high as 2950 rpm [6]. The appropriate peripheral speed is 50 m/s for SRM rotors and 15-20 m/s for Sigma rotors. The diameter D of the rotor and the ratio between the length L and the diameter of the rotors are the defining dimensions for these volumetric machines [7]. V_i describes the geometry of each individual compressor, and the maximum yield η_{max} is

attained when $\pi_c = V_i^k$, where π_c is the compression ratio and k is the adiabatic index value dependent on the nature of the working agent [8]. There are the following recommendations:

- $V_i=2.5$ for air conditioning and heat pumps ($\pi_c \approx 5$)
- $V_i=3.5$ for cooling processes ($\pi_c \approx 8$)
- $V_i=5$ for freezing at low temperatures ($\pi_c \approx 15$)

Screw compressors are high-efficiency devices that compress various working fluids used in industry. A screw compressor's working chamber is formed between the rotors' lobes sections and the casing, which shrinks as the rotors revolve, carrying out the compression process [9]. Figure 1 depicts a Computer-Aided Design (CAD) model of a screw compressor. Clearances between the rotors and between the rotors and the casing must be kept to a minimum for optimal compression. To ensure thermal expansion, these clearances for compressors with oil injection can be on the order of 40 μm , and for those without injection, they can be of the order of 100 μm [10].

In the research and development of new innovative products [11] that can be introduced to the market, the use of numerical approaches in the design process has come to represent a particularly significant step [12]. Computational

Fluid Dynamics (CFD) approaches have recently been extensively employed to assess the performance of a volumetric machine with positive displacement. The use of finite volume techniques entails meshing the computational domain for the unsteady, three-dimensional modeling of flow through a screw compressor [13-14]. Even though the concept of a screw compressor is relatively new, studies on the thermodynamics of screw compressors have been conducted with the goal of developing a mathematical model. These models were used to both analyze and optimize the profiles of the rotor lobes [15-17]. The performance of such a machine may be predicted using CFD techniques. These approaches are used in the study of flow in screw compressors to investigate unstable flows with shifting boundaries.

Authors in [18] investigated the flow into the screw compressors with similar limits. A particularly critical issue occurs when utilizing finite volume techniques to examine the flow through screw compressors, especially the formation of the computation grid for unsteady simulations with grid motions. The calculating grid must deform in the same way that the volumes in the compressor vary with the rotation of the rotors. It has been shown [19, 20] that no commercial grid generation software is currently capable of achieving this. Despite this, only a few reports of unsteady flow in 3D for screw compressors with large discharge pressures [21-22] have been published.

Fig. 1. 3D CAD screw compressor model.

The numerical complexity of multiphase flow (gas and oil) via small gaps on the order of tens of microns [23] is also carried to the following components of a screw compressor compression station [24]. As a result, the process of separating gas from oil becomes a separate issue that requires specific attention [25]. This may be accomplished by employing separators with porous material filters [26], capable of retaining oil droplets as small as 0.1 microns [27]. An oil-injected screw compressor with a compression ratio larger than 9 in a single stage was mathematically investigated in this paper. The generation of the calculation grid for the rotor domain [28], the setting of the multiphase case [29], and the stabilization of the solver by using an initialization file [30] in which the flow through a screw compressor without oil injection was analyzed were among the challenges of this analysis.

II. GRID GENERATION

Using a combination of structured and unstructured meshes, the working domain of a screw compressor may be discretized. The rotor domain, the pressure domain, and the suction domain are each represented by one of the three subdomains of the flow domain. The whole grid of a screw compressor can be seen in Figure 2. Grids that combine structured and unstructured elements can be used to discretize stator domains. But in order to create the computation grid for the rotor domain, specialized software is required. TwinMesh [29] is specifically designed for positive displacement machines with two rotors that are arranged in parallel planes and have complicated geometries. The common IGES format or a CSV-type file is used for the geometry input. Two meshed rotors with O-grid grids that are joined via an interface make up the typical topology. Such a topology is seen in Figure 3.

Fig. 2. Screw compressor mesh.

Fig. 3. TwinMesh-based 2d computational grid topology.

With the rotor and casing curves imported, the TwinMesh program creates 2D meshes for various rotor locations. The software builds an interface between the two rotors and initializes an O-grid for each rotor for each 2D grid [30].

Explicit and iterative techniques are used to smooth out the original grids. These techniques are based on standards such as the uniform distribution of nodes on the border, the growth ratio of the elements, the element's minimum angle, etc. [31]. The user defines the number of elements, which is directly influenced by the node distribution throughout the geometry. Figure 4 displays the grid's quality, with the red parts denoting the lower-quality components.

Fig. 4. Mesh quality.

For all 2D grids related to rotation angles, the quality of the computation grid may be checked (minimum angle, determinant, growth rate, change of volumes, etc.). The 3D grid is created with improved resolution when all 2D grids have been finished. In general, the criteria for evaluating the quality of calculation grids for volumetric machines with positive displacement [32] are based on the following:

- the grid must accurately represent the fluid domain
- the internal angle must be greater than 18° and the element distribution must be uniform
- small changes in the position of the nodes for two consecutive angles
- the number of grids per rotation must be adequate, preferably from degree to degree

Since all 3D grids have the same grid topology and number of nodes, the CFD solver can handle deformed grids without interpolation by applying just conservation rules. The number of elements and their types for each subdomain are shown in Table I.

TABLE I. MESH STATISTICS

No.	Subdomain	No. of nodes	No. of elements		
			Tetrahedral	Pyramid	Hexahedral
1.	Rotor	2223350	-	-	2097120
2.	Suction	438460	1792222	1805	88445
3.	Discharge	197161	534856	1805	88445
4.	Injection pipe	89300	-	-	85652
5.	TOTAL	2948271	4690350		

III. CFD ANALYSIS

The choice of the ANSYS CFX software for the modeling of such a complicated flow was made due to the wide variety of numerical models at its disposal. The following parameters are used with volumetric machines:

- Grid deformation: since the grid movement is taken into account by the differential equations, interpolation is not required. Instead, FORTRAN code is used to read the grids from TwinMesh and calculate the movement.
- The complex properties of working fluids, such as non-Newtonian fluids or fluids with high viscosity, ideal or real gas models, etc.
- The multi-phase models, such as the water or oil injection in screw compressors.
- The heat transfer model, i.e. the thermal transfer from fluid to solid and vice versa.
- The turbulence models, such as the Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes models and scale-resolving models.

The description of the rotor movement, the definition of the suction domain, the discharge domain, along with the oil inlet ports, and the definition of the interfaces between the domains all come first when setting up the case for simulating the flow through a screw compressor. Figure 5 shows the geometry of the CLP180-type rotors employed in these simulations, with five "male" lobes and six "female" lobes. The rotors have a 412.45 mm length, a 180 mm space between their two axes, and rotate at 3343 rpm for "male". The distance between the rotors is approximately $20 \mu\text{m}$, while the distance between the rotors and the housing is around $50 \mu\text{m}$.

Fig. 5. Rotors shapes with surface mesh.

The oil used was TURBIN YAGI 68, whose physical projections (molar mass, density, specific heat capacity, reference temperature, reference pressure, reference specific enthalpy, reference specific entropy, dynamic viscosity, and thermal conductivity) were established experimentally [33]. The working fluid was selected as ideal gas air, and the turbulence model used was the SST (Shear-Stress Transport). The time step for the unsteady analysis was determined by the speed of the screw compressor. Figure 6 depicts the boundary constraints that ANSYS CFX Pre imposes in order to make the mathematical approach as realistic as possible. At the inlet and outlet, where the pressure was applied (1 bar for the inlet and 9 bars for the outflow), "opening" conditions are therefore mandated. For the oil port inlet condition volume II's pressure (2.5 bar) was enforced. In order to assess the pressure in the four volumes that develop at the start of the compression process, four monitoring points were created for real-time monitoring. These dots can be seen in Figure 6 (right).

Fig. 6. Ansys CFX Pre boundary conditions.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

This analysis's goal is to ascertain how oil injection impacts a screw compressor's performance. This led to the analysis of a compressor with an intake pressure of 1 bar and a discharge pressure of 9 bars. The distributions of pressures and speeds in certain planes, as well as changes in flow and pressure at the compressor's intake and exit, are depicted in Figures 7-8.

Fig. 7. Absolute pressure location: (a) 0, (b) 18, (c) 36, and (d) 54 degrees.

Fig. 8. Oil volume fraction: (a) 0, (b) 18, (c) 36, and (d) 54 degrees.

Fig. 9. Absolute pressure evolution through all four chambers.

Fig. 10. Mass flow variation per one complete revolution.

Fig. 11. Volumetric efficiency.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Numerous challenges arise when analyzing multiphase flows when they are conducted in extremely tiny areas, especially in the scale of microns. For several geometrical and physical features that the volumetric machine, the screw compressor with oil injection, exhibits, it is challenging to develop hypotheses regarding the numerical analysis.

In this paper, the challenge is doubled by the fact that we are dealing with a high pressure ratio, 9, in a single stage. The flow was examined using TwinMesh grid generation software, and the flow's underlying equation system was solved using Ansys CFX. As a result, real-time monitoring of the absolute pressure in each of the four volumes was produced when the compression process began. The fluctuation of the absolute pressure and the flow rate from the compressor's intake to its exit are among the findings. Also, the volumetric efficiency was determined numerically, and for pressure ratio equal to 9, was 71%. The numerical analysis is a crucial step in the creation of new screw compressors since it reveals significant data about their efficiency.

The originality of this work lies in the numerical modeling of an oil-injected screw compressor that can achieve a compression ratio larger than 9 in a single step. Unfortunately, most studies terminate at pressure ratios of up to 3–4 due to the solver's instability. To the best of our knowledge, there are no studies that mention such flows (biphase with significant pressure gradients). Due to this, in the future research, experimental testing series will be carried out to validate the numerical results. These tests will be carried out on the testing facility [34] for screw compressors that the Romanian Research and Development Institute for Gas Turbines (COMOTI has. The setup is shown in Figure 12.

Fig. 12. Experimental testing facility.

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REFERENCES

- [1] W. Wu and Z. Zhang, "Development of single screw compressor technologies and their tendency," *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part E: Journal of Process Mechanical Engineering*, vol. 236, no. 2, pp. 738–751, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1177/09544089211043011>.
- [2] N. Stošić, "Review Article: Screw Compressors in Refrigeration and Air Conditioning," *HVAC&R Research*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 233–263, Jul. 2004, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10789669.2004.10391102>.

- [3] F. L. Yuditskii, B. L. Grinpress, and Yu. L. Semenov, "Dismountable end face seal for screw compressors," *Chemical and Petroleum Engineering*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 167–168, Feb. 1971, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01146549>.
- [4] M. Nitulescu *et al.*, "New projects developed by COMOTI in gas industry," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 90, no. 1, Apr. 2015, Art. no. 012015, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/90/1/012015>.
- [5] M. Chamoun, R. Rulliere, P. Haberschill, and J.-L. Peureux, "Modelica-based modeling and simulation of a twin screw compressor for heat pump applications," *Applied Thermal Engineering*, vol. 58, no. 1, pp. 479–489, Sep. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2013.04.020>.
- [6] D. Hairston, "Rotary screw compressors reduce energy consumption. (Focus on: fans, blowers & compressors)," *Chemical Engineering*, vol. 109, no. 12, pp. 39–40, Nov. 2002.
- [7] T. N. Mustafin, R. R. Yakupova, A. V. Burmistrova, M. S. Khamidullina, and I. G. Khisameeva, "Analysis of Influence of Screw Compressor Construction Parameters and Working Condition on Rotor Temperature Fields," *Procedia Engineering*, vol. 152, pp. 423–433, Jan. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2016.07.612>.
- [8] P. Harnatkiewicz, E. Rusinski, and P. Moczko, "The lifetime prediction of a rotary screw compressor of a liquid cooler subjected to high pressure and high frequency loads," *Engineering Failure Analysis*, vol. 17, no. 6, pp. 1290–1299, Sep. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engfailanal.2010.03.003>.
- [9] J. Li, H. Wu, B. Wang, Z. Xing, and P. Shu, "Research on the performance of water-injection twin screw compressor," *Applied Thermal Engineering*, vol. 29, no. 16, pp. 3401–3408, Nov. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2009.05.018>.
- [10] T. Tam *et al.*, "Experimental Investigation of Screw Compressor Clearance Monitoring Techniques," in *26th International Compressor Engineering Conference at Purdue*, Jul. 2022, Art. no. 1136.
- [11] P. Salami, Y. Ajabshirchi, S. Abdollahpoor, and H. Behfar, "A Comparison Among Different Parameters for the Design of a Photovoltaic/Thermal System Using Computational Fluid Dynamics," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 6, no. 5, pp. 1119–1123, Oct. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.667>.
- [12] A. C. Mangra, "Design and Numerical Analysis of a Micro Gas Turbine Combustion Chamber," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 6422–6426, Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3835>.
- [13] A. Spille-Kohoff, J. Hesse, and A. E. Shorbagy, "CFD simulation of a screw compressor including leakage flows and rotor heating," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 90, no. 1, Apr. 2015, Art. no. 012009, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/90/1/012009>.
- [14] H. Ding and Y. Jiang, "CFD simulation of a screw compressor with oil injection," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 232, no. 1, Dec. 2017, Art. no. 012020, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/232/1/012020>.
- [15] T. W. Bein and J. F. Hamilton, "Computer Modeling of an Oil Flooded Single Screw Air Compressor," in *International Compressor Engineering Conference*, 1982, Art. no. 383.
- [16] W. W. Boblitt and J. Moore, "Computer Modeling of Single-Screw Oil Flooded Refrigerant Compressors," in *International Compressor Engineering Conference*, 1984, Art. no. 506.
- [17] W. Jianhua and J. Guangxi, "The Computer Simulation of Oil-Flooded Single Screw Compressors," *International Compressor Engineering Conference*, Jan. 1988, Art. no. 362.
- [18] I. Demirdžić and M. Perić, "Finite volume method for prediction of fluid flow in arbitrarily shaped domains with moving boundaries," *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Fluids*, vol. 10, no. 7, pp. 771–790, 1990, <https://doi.org/10.1002/flid.1650100705>.
- [19] A. Kovacevic, "Boundary adaptation in grid generation for CFD analysis of screw compressors," *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, vol. 64, no. 3, pp. 401–426, 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1002/nme.1376>.
- [20] B. G. S. Prasad, "CFD for Positive Displacement Compressors," in *International Compressor Engineering Conference*, 2004, Art. no. 1689.
- [21] I. Malael and M. Sima, "Numerical Investigation of a Screw Compressor Performance," *TURBO*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 25–30, Dec. 2017.
- [22] M. Ion, D. Valeriu, G. B. George, P. Ionut, and Ș. A. Ștefan, "Numerical Efficiency Evaluation of a High Pressure Ratio Screw Compressor," in *2018 5th International Conference on Mathematics and Computers in Sciences and Industry (MCSI)*, Corfu, Greece, Dec. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MCSI.2018.00009>.
- [23] S. Tomescu and I. O. Bucur, "Numerical Investigation of Oil Gas Separation with the Use of VOF CFD," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 7841–7845, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4446>.
- [24] S. Tomescu, M. Enache, N. Visan, and F. Florean, "Experimental Measurements Using Shadowgraph System on the Screw Compressor," *UPB Scientific Bulletin, Series D*, vol. 84, no. 1, pp. 77–86, 2022.
- [25] S. Tomescu, V. Petrescu, A. Serban, and S. Voicu, "Energy Efficiency of an Oil Injected Screw Compressor Operating at Various Discharge Pressures," in *2021 10th International Conference on Energy and Environment (CIEM)*, Bucharest, Romania, Jul. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CIEM52821.2021.9614754>.
- [26] N. P. Mahmoud and A. Zabihi, "Numerical Simulation of a Single-Phase Flow Through Fractures with Permeable, Porous and Non-Ductile Walls," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 5, pp. 2041–2046, Oct. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1448>.
- [27] F. Chen *et al.*, "Development and coalescence mechanism of an improved filter cartridge for oil mist separators," *Chemical Engineering Research and Design*, vol. 187, pp. 306–318, Nov. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cherd.2022.09.008>.
- [28] A. Spille and J. Hesse, "Structured meshes and reliable CFD simulations: TwinMesh for positive displacement machines," in *International VDI Conference Screw Machines*, Dortmund, Germany, Sep. 2014.
- [29] I. Malael, I. O. Bucur, and C. Slujitoru, "Numerical Investigation of the Minimum Gap Impact on the Screw Compressor Efficiency," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 916, no. 1, Jun. 2020, Art. no. 012057, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/916/1/012057>.
- [30] R. Andres, J. Hesse, and A. Spille, "Investigation of radial gap size change under load and the impact on performance for a twin screw compressor using numerical simulation," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 1267, no. 1, Aug. 2022, Art. no. 012007, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/1267/1/012007>.
- [31] "TwinMesh | Reliable CFD analysis of rotary pd machines," *TwinMesh*. <https://www.twinmesh.com/>.
- [32] R. Andres, J. Hesse, F. Hetze, and D. Low, "Cfd simulation of a two stage twin screw compressor including leakage flows and comparison with experimental data," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 425, no. 1, Jun. 2018, Art. no. 012018, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/425/1/012018>.
- [33] S. Rane, A. Kovačević, and N. Stošić, "Analytical Grid Generation for accurate representation of clearances in CFD for Screw Machines," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 90, no. 1, Apr. 2015, Art. no. 012008, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/90/1/012008>.
- [34] S. Rane, A. Kovacevic, N. Stosic, and M. Kethidi, "Grid deformation strategies for CFD analysis of screw compressors," *International Journal of Refrigeration*, vol. 36, no. 7, pp. 1883–1893, Nov. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijrefrig.2013.04.008>.
- [35] L. Olarasu, M. Stoicescu, I. Malureanu, and I. Onutu, "Considerations for Using a Hydraulic Fracturing Fluid for Breaking Crude Oil Emulsion from Reservoir," *Revista de Chimie*, vol. 69, no. 6, pp. 1498–1500, Jul. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.37358/RC.18.6.6354>.
- [36] "Oil-injected screw compressors for natural gas, air, CO₂, N₂ and other," *COMOTI - Romanian Research and Development Institute for Gas Turbines*. <http://www.comoti.ro/en/Comprosoare-cu-surub.htm>.

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An Improved Correction Technique for the Prediction of the Dynamic Response of a Beam under a Moving Vehicle

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ABSTRACT

This study presents a correction approach that can capture the discontinuities in the bending moment and shear force in the dynamic analysis of beam-like structures traveled by a moving vehicle. The proposed approach was based on the Dynamic Modal Acceleration Method (DyMAM) to correct the dynamic response of the supporting structure with a reduced number of vibration modes. The use of a two-axle vehicle model was adopted to consider the pitching effect in the presence of surface irregularity and damping. The interacting forces between the beam and vehicle were filtered to avoid undesirable high-frequency contributions. Subsequently, a new formulation for the entire vehicle-beam system was obtained. The corresponding equation was solved using the Newmark numerical scheme to obtain the system responses in each time step. A numerical example was illustrated, showing that the proposed method was in close agreement with previous correction solutions in the vehicle-beam interaction analysis.

Keywords-moving vehicle; vehicle-bridge interaction; dynamic modal acceleration method; modal equations of motion

I. INTRODUCTION

Vibration analysis of beam-like structures is an interesting aspect of structural design [1-2]. The study of the dynamic response of a beam induced by a moving load has long been an attractive topic [3-5]. The traditional Modal Displacement Method (MDM) is a widespread approach to determine the dynamic response of a beam and analyze Vehicle Beam Interaction (VBI) systems [6-10]. In MDM, the solution is obtained as a series expansion in terms of the eigenfunctions of the distributed system without damping and loading, having the advantage that the response quantities can be determined by the superposition of only a few first modes possessing low frequencies. Unfortunately, the exclusion of high-frequency modes leads to significant errors in the calculation of strains and stresses [11]. Once considering the bending moment and the shear force distribution of the beam, the MDM-based approach does not show the effectiveness of capturing the

discontinuity and the jump of internal forces diagrams at the points where the vehicle axles are applied.

Several Modal Correction Methods (MCMs) have been proposed to involve the contribution of truncated higher-order modes to the structural response, such as the Mode Acceleration Method (MAM) [11-12], the Dynamic Correction Method (DCM) [13-14], and the Force Derivative Method (FDM) [15-16]. To the best of our knowledge, a limited amount of research has applied MCMs to VBI analysis. In [17-18], computational procedures were developed to analyze the dynamic response of a beam to single or multiple moving oscillators. The solution was the sum of modal series representation and quasistatic response. In [19-20], an approach based on DCM was introduced, aiming to consider the inertial, damping, and gravitational effects of moving masses and oscillators. In [21], a correction procedure was presented, in which the system response was separated into response components of low- and high-frequency contribution. These MCMs significantly improved the accuracy of structural

dynamic response computations for the MDM when using a reduced set of eigenvectors. However, the effectiveness of MAM decreases in the case of high-frequency content loading. The solution provided in [20] seems to be quite mathematically cumbersome. In the procedure exploited in [21], the described correction method could fail when the loading function cannot be expressed in analytical form. Such problems have resulted in inconvenience in the computational process.

To overcome the limits of the above-mentioned MCMs, a MAM variant called the Dynamic Modal Acceleration Method (DyMAM) was presented, which can be used for both discrete and continuous structural systems [22]. The main idea of this approach was to introduce an additional dummy oscillator to filter each dynamic load on the structure to avoid undesirable high-frequency contributions. The output of this filter was used to correct the responses of the structure given by MDM. Due to the simple implementation and the fewer requirements in the excessive application, DyMAM can be operated in both deterministic and random dynamic loading cases [22]. As observed, no extension of this technique to predict the dynamic response of continuous structures traveled by a moving system has been carried out.

In this study, the DyMAM procedure was extended for dynamic response analysis of a beam-like structure subjected to a moving vehicle. It is possible to estimate the response of the supporting structure by using fewer eigenfunctions, avoiding a more cumbersome solving procedure. The vehicle was idealized as a rigid bar with two degrees of freedom and linked to the beam through two independent suspension units and tires set by linear mass-spring-damper systems. The interacting force caused by the vehicle axle on the beam was filtered through an elementary dynamic system. The equation of motion of the coupled VBI system based on a semi-analytical approach was established. Then, the dynamic response of the VBI system was obtained using the Newmark numerical scheme, which makes it easier to speed up the analysis. The advantage of the suggested method was shown by considering the quasistatic effect and capturing the stress discontinuities caused by the moving vehicle. Therefore, DyMAM provides a convenient procedure to improve accuracy in VBI analysis.

II. THEORETICAL MODELING OF THE VBI SYSTEM

A. Vehicle's Equations of Motion

Figure 1 shows the considered two-axle vehicle model. The vehicle body is simplified as a rigid bar and can move vertically by v_c and rotate ϕ_c around its center of mass. The terms m_c and J_c stand for mass and moment of inertia, respectively. Each wheel is represented by one vertical motion $v_{w,i}$, the corresponding mass $m_{w,i}$, and the tire characteristics including $k_{w,i}$ and $c_{w,i}$. The suspension unit is described by a linear spring dashpot with a stiffness coefficient $k_{s,i}$ and a damping coefficient $c_{s,i}$. The vehicle is assumed to run horizontally along the beam at a constant speed V , and L_i is the horizontal distance of the i -th axle to the center of the vehicle body.

Fig. 1. The vehicle model moving along a beam.

Using D'Alembert's principle, the vehicle's equations of motion body are written as follows:

$$m_c \ddot{v}_c + c_{s,1}(\dot{v}_c - \dot{v}_{w,1} + \dot{\phi}_c L_1) + k_{s,1}(v_c - v_{w,1} + \phi_c L_1) + c_{s,2}(\dot{v}_c - \dot{v}_{w,2} - \dot{\phi}_c L_2) + k_{s,2}(v_c - v_{w,2} - \phi_c L_2) = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$J_c \ddot{\phi}_c + c_{s,1} L_1 (\dot{v}_c - \dot{v}_{w,1} + \dot{\phi}_c L_1) + k_{s,1} L_1 (v_c - v_{w,1} + \phi_c L_1) - c_{s,2} L_2 (\dot{v}_c - \dot{v}_{w,2} - \dot{\phi}_c L_2) - k_{s,2} L_2 (v_c - v_{w,2} - \phi_c L_2) = 0 \quad (2)$$

The equations of motion of the wheels:

$$m_{w,1} \ddot{v}_{w,1} + c_{s,1}(\dot{v}_{w,1} - \dot{v}_c - \dot{\phi}_c L_1) + k_{s,1}(v_{w,1} - v_c - \phi_c L_1) + c_{w,1}(\dot{v}_{w,1} - \dot{v}_{b,1}) + k_{w,1}(v_{w,1} - v_{b,1}) = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$m_{w,2} \ddot{v}_{w,2} + c_{s,2}(\dot{v}_{w,2} - \dot{v}_c + \dot{\phi}_c L_2) + k_{s,2}(v_{w,2} - v_c + \phi_c L_2) + c_{w,2}(\dot{v}_{w,2} - \dot{v}_{b,2}) + k_{w,2}(v_{w,2} - v_{b,2}) = 0 \quad (4)$$

where the over-dot denotes the derivative quantities for time t , $v_{b,i}$ is the vertical displacement at the contact point between the i -th axle and the surface of the bridge. The interaction force $f_{c,i}$ caused by the i -th axle to the beam is given by:

$$f_{c,i} = c_{w,i}(\dot{v}_{w,i} - \dot{v}_{b,i}) + k_{w,i}(v_{w,i} - v_{b,i}) + m_{w,i}g + r_i m_c g \quad (5)$$

where r_i is the weight distribution coefficient of the vehicle body on the i -th wheel under a static load of vehicle self-weight $r_1 = \frac{L_2}{(L_1+L_2)}$ and $r_2 = \frac{L_1}{(L_1+L_2)}$, and g denotes the acceleration of gravity. The vertical displacement at the contact point $v_{b,i}$ is given by:

$$v_{b,i} = [w(x, t) + \lambda(x)]|_{x=x_i(t)} = \chi_i w(x_i(t), t) + \lambda(x_i(t)) \quad (6)$$

$$\dot{v}_{b,i} = \left. \frac{d[v_{b,i}(x, t)]}{dt} \right|_{x=x_i(t)} = \chi_i \frac{\partial w(x_i(t), t)}{\partial t} + \chi_i \frac{\partial w(x_i(t), t)}{\partial x} \dot{x}_i(t) + \frac{d\lambda(x_i(t))}{dx} \dot{x}_i(t) = \chi_i \dot{w}(x_i(t), t) + \chi_i w'(x_i(t), t) \dot{x}_i(t) + \lambda'(x_i(t)) \dot{x}_i(t) \quad (7)$$

where the over prime means space derivative, $w(x_i(t), t)$ and $\lambda(x_i(t))$ are the vertical displacement and the surface roughness of the bridge corresponding to $x_i(t)$, that represents the location of the i -th axle in the structural coordinate system over time. χ_i is called the window function that describes the appearance of the axle of the vehicle on the bridge, which can be conveniently adopted by [20]:

$$\chi_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } 0 \leq x_i(t) \leq L, \\ 0 & \text{for } x_i(t) < 0 \text{ or } x_i(t) > L \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

B. The Equations of Motion of the Bridge using the Dynamic Modal Acceleration Method (DyMAM)

The partial differential equation of an elastic Euler-Bernoulli uniform beam subjected to a moving load can be expressed as:

$$\mu \frac{\partial^2 w(x,t)}{\partial t^2} + D(x,t) + EI \frac{\partial^4 w(x,t)}{\partial x^4} = \sum_{i=1}^2 \chi_i f_{c,i} \delta[x - x_i(t)] \tag{9}$$

where EI , μ and $D(x, t)$ are flexural rigidity mass per unit of length and damping force per unit length of beam, respectively, and $\delta[]$ denotes the Dirac's delta function. Using the modal displacement method, the approximate solution of (9) can be represented as the superposition of the first N_m modal shapes of the beam:

$$w(x, t) = \sum_{n=1}^{N_m} W_n(x) T_n(t) = W^T(x) T(t) = w_{MDM}(x, t) \tag{10}$$

$$W(x) = \langle W_1(x) \dots W_n(x) \dots W_{N_m}(x) \rangle^T \tag{11}$$

$$T(t) = \langle T_1(t) \dots T_n(t) \dots T_{N_m}(t) \rangle^T \tag{12}$$

where $T_n(t)$ is the generalized modal coordinates, $W_n(x)$ is the normal vibration mode which is determined simultaneously with the n -th modal circular frequency ω_n as the solution of the eigenvalue problem:

$$\mu \omega_n^2 W_n(x) = EI \frac{d^4}{dx^4} W_n(x) \tag{13}$$

$W_n(x)$ satisfies the boundary conditions and the orthogonality property:

$$\int_0^L \mu W_n(x) W_m(x) dx = \delta_{nm} \tag{14}$$

where δ_{nm} is the Kronecker delta. Substituting (10) into (9), then multiplying both parts of (9) by $W_m(x)$, and integrating into the range $[0, L]$, results in:

$$\ddot{T}_n(t) + 2\xi_n \omega_n \dot{T}_n(t) + \omega_n^2 T_n(t) = \sum_{i=1}^2 \chi_i f_{c,i} W_n(x_i(t)) \tag{15}$$

where ξ_n is the damping ratio in the n -th mode of vibration, and $W_n(x_i(t))$ stands for the n -th normal vibration mode at $x_i(t)$. Equation (15) can be expressed in matrix form:

$$\ddot{T} + \kappa \dot{T} + \Omega^2 T = W_L(x(t)) X f_c \tag{16}$$

where:

$$\kappa = \text{diag}[2\xi_n \omega_n] \tag{17}$$

$$\Omega = \text{diag}[\omega_n] \tag{18}$$

$$X = \text{diag}[\chi_i] \tag{19}$$

$$W_L(x(t)) = \begin{bmatrix} W_1(x_1(t)) & W_1(x_2(t)) \\ \dots & \dots \\ W_n(x_1(t)) & W_n(x_2(t)) \\ \dots & \dots \\ W_{N_m}(x_1(t)) & W_{N_m}(x_2(t)) \end{bmatrix} \tag{20}$$

$$f_c = \begin{Bmatrix} f_{c,1} \\ f_{c,2} \end{Bmatrix} \tag{21}$$

where $\text{diag}[]$ defines the diagonal matrix. According to the DyMAM, the displacement of the beam can be expressed as [22]:

$$w(x, t) = w_{MDM}(x, t) + \Delta w_{DyMAM}(x, t) = W^T(x) T(t) + Z^T(x) H(t) = w_{DyMAM}(x, t) \tag{22}$$

where $H(t)$ is the filter dynamic loading vector, and $Z(x)$ is the time-dependent vector collecting the residual flexibility matrix.

$$Z(x) = \langle Z(x, x_1(t)) \quad Z(x, x_2(t)) \rangle^T \tag{23}$$

$$H(t) = \langle H_1(t) \quad H_2(t) \rangle^T \tag{24}$$

where:

$$Z(x, x_j(t)) = G(x, x_j(t)) \chi_j - \sum_{n=1}^{N_m} \frac{1}{\omega_n^2} W_n(x) W_n(x_j(t)) \chi_j \tag{25}$$

where $G(x, x_j(t))$ presents the static Green's function of the beam that is the solution of (26) with appropriate boundary conditions.

$$EI \frac{d^4}{dx^4} G(x, x_j(t)) = \delta[x - x_j(t)] \tag{26}$$

$H(t)$ is determined as the solution of the following equation:

$$\ddot{H} + \bar{\kappa} \dot{H} + \bar{\Omega}^2 H = \bar{\Omega}^2 X f_c \tag{27}$$

where:

$$\bar{\kappa} = \text{diag}[2\xi_1 \bar{\omega}_1 \quad 2\xi_2 \bar{\omega}_2] \tag{28}$$

$$\bar{\Omega} = \text{diag}[\bar{\omega}_1 \quad \bar{\omega}_2] \tag{29}$$

where $\bar{\omega}_i$ is the circular frequency of the filter associated with the dynamic load of the i -th axle, while ξ_i is the viscous damping ratio for the i -th filter, which is computed according to Rayleigh's damping.

$\bar{\omega}_j =$

$$\begin{cases} \sqrt{\frac{EI \int_0^L \left[\frac{d^2}{dx^2} G(x, x_j(t)) \right]^2 dx - \Phi_j^T \Omega^2 \Phi_j}{\mu \int_0^L G^2(x, x_j(t)) dx - \Phi_j^T \Phi_j}} & \text{for } 0 \leq x_j(t) \leq L, \\ 0 & \text{for } x_j(t) < 0 \text{ or } x_j(t) > L \end{cases} \tag{30}$$

$$\bar{\xi}_j = \frac{1}{2\bar{\omega}_j} \theta_M + \frac{\bar{\omega}_j}{2} \theta_K \tag{31}$$

$$\Phi_j = \mu \int_0^L W(x) G(x, x_j(t)) dx \tag{32}$$

$$\theta_M = \frac{2}{\omega_{N_m}^2 - \omega_1^2} \omega_1 \omega_{N_m} (\omega_{N_m} \xi_1 - \omega_1 \xi_{N_m}) \tag{33}$$

$$\theta_K = \frac{2(\omega_{N_m} \xi_{N_m} - \omega_1 \xi_1)}{\omega_{N_m}^2 - \omega_1^2} \tag{34}$$

C. The Equations of Motion of the VBI System

Based on DyMAM, the vertical displacement of the bridge corresponding to $x_i(t)$ is expressed as follows:

$$w(x_i(t), t) \approx \sum_{n=1}^{N_m} W_n(x_i(t))T_n(t) + \sum_{j=1}^2 Z(x_i(t), x_j(t))H_j(t) \quad (35)$$

The partial derivative of the displacement can be written as:

$$\dot{w}(x_i(t), t) \approx \sum_{n=1}^{N_m} W_n(x_i(t))\dot{T}_n(t) + \sum_{j=1}^2 Z_j(x_i(t), x_j(t))\dot{H}_j(t) \quad (36)$$

$$w'(x_i(t), t) \approx \sum_{n=1}^{N_m} W'_n(x_i(t))T_n(t) + \sum_{j=1}^2 Z'_j(x_i(t), x_j(t))H_j(t) \quad (37)$$

$$\dot{x}_i(t) = \frac{dx_i(t)}{dt} = V \quad (38)$$

Substituting (36)-(38) into (6)-(7) results in:

$$v_{b,i} = \chi_i \sum_{n=1}^{N_m} W_n(x_i(t))T_n(t) + \chi_i \sum_{j=1}^2 Z(x_i(t), x_j(t))H_j(t) + \lambda(x_i(t)) \quad (39)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{v}_{b,i} = & \chi_i \sum_{n=1}^{N_m} W_n(x_i(t))\dot{T}_n(t) + \chi_i \dot{x}_i(t) \sum_{n=1}^{N_m} W'_n(x_i(t))T_n(t) \\ & + \dot{x}_i(t)\lambda'(x_i(t)) + \chi_i \sum_{j=1}^2 Z'(x_i(t), x_j(t))\dot{H}_j(t) \\ & + \chi_i \dot{x}_i(t) \sum_{j=1}^2 Z'(x_i(t), x_j(t))H_j(t) \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

Substituting (39)-(40) into (1)-(4) and after combining with (5) leads to the following equations of motion of the coupled VBI system in modal space, written symbolically as:

$$M\ddot{u} + C\dot{u} + Ku = P \quad (41)$$

where M , C , and K are the mass matrix, damping matrix, and stiffness matrix of the coupled vehicle-bridge system, respectively, u , \dot{u} and \ddot{u} denote the displacement, velocity, and acceleration vectors, respectively, and P denotes the force vector. To make the presentation clear in (41), the submatrices, subcolumn, and sub-row vectors will be denoted by quantities enclosed by $[]$, $\{ \}$, and $\langle \rangle$, respectively.

The matrices are defined as follows:

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} [I]_{N_m \times N_m} & [0] & \{0\} & \{0\} & [M_w]_{N_m \times 2} \\ [0] & [I]_{2 \times 2} & \{0\} & \{0\} & [\bar{M}_w]_{2 \times 2} \\ \langle 0 \rangle & \langle 0 \rangle & m_c & 0 & \langle 0 \rangle \\ \langle 0 \rangle & \langle 0 \rangle & 0 & J_c & \langle 0 \rangle \\ [0]_{2 \times N_m} & [0]_{2 \times 2} & \{0\} & \{0\} & diag[m_{w,i}]_{2 \times 2} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$u = \begin{Bmatrix} T(t) \\ H(t) \\ v_c \\ \varphi_c \\ \{v_{w,i}\} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (42)$$

where $[I]$ is the identity matrix.

$$[M_w] = \begin{bmatrix} m_{1,1} & m_{1,2} \\ \dots & \dots \\ m_{n,1} & m_{n,2} \\ \dots & \dots \\ m_{N_m,1} & m_{N_m,2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (43)$$

with $m_{n,i} = m_{w,i}W_n(x_i(t))\chi_i$.

$$[\bar{M}_w] = diag[\bar{m}_i], \text{ with } \bar{m}_i = m_{w,i}\bar{\omega}_i^2\chi_i \quad (44)$$

$C =$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \kappa_{N_m \times N_m} & [0] & \{C_v\} & \{C_\varphi\} & [C_s]_{N_m \times 2} \\ [0] & \bar{\kappa}_{2 \times 2} & \{\bar{C}_v\} & \{\bar{C}_\varphi\} & [\bar{C}_s]_{2 \times 2} \\ (0) & (0) & \sum_{i=1}^2 c_{s,i} & c_{s,1}L_1 - c_{s,2}L_2 & \langle C_{sp} \rangle \\ (0) & (0) & c_{s,1}L_1 - c_{s,2}L_2 & \sum_{i=1}^2 c_{s,i}L_i^2 & \langle C_{sq} \rangle \\ [C_w]_{2 \times N_m} & [\bar{C}_w]_{2 \times 2} & \langle C_{sp} \rangle^T & \langle C_{sq} \rangle^T & diag[c_{s,i} + c_{w,i}]_{2 \times 2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (45)$$

$$\{C_v\} = \langle c_1^v \dots c_n^v \dots c_{N_m}^v \rangle^T \quad (46)$$

with $c_n^v = -\sum_{i=1}^2 c_{s,i}W_n(x_i(t))\chi_i$.

$$\{C_\varphi\} = \langle c_1^\varphi \dots c_n^\varphi \dots c_{N_m}^\varphi \rangle^T \quad (47)$$

with $c_n^\varphi = -c_{s,1}L_1W_n(x_1(t))\chi_1 + c_{s,2}L_2W_n(x_2(t))\chi_2$.

$$[C_s] = \begin{bmatrix} c_{1,1}^s & c_{1,2}^s \\ \dots & \dots \\ c_{n,1}^s & c_{n,2}^s \\ \dots & \dots \\ c_{N_m,1}^s & c_{N_m,2}^s \end{bmatrix} \quad (48)$$

with $c_{n,i}^s = c_{s,i}W_n(x_i(t))\chi_i$.

$$\{\bar{C}_v\} = \langle \bar{c}_1^v \dots \bar{c}_2^v \rangle^T \text{ with } \bar{c}_i^v = -c_{s,i}\bar{\omega}_i^2\chi_i \quad (49)$$

$$\{\bar{C}_\varphi\} = \langle -\bar{c}_1^\varphi \dots \bar{c}_2^\varphi \rangle^T \text{ with } \bar{c}_i^\varphi = c_{s,i}\bar{\omega}_i^2\chi_i \quad (50)$$

$$[\bar{C}_s] = diag[\bar{c}_i^s] \text{ with } \bar{c}_i^s = c_{s,i}\bar{\omega}_i^2\chi_i \quad (51)$$

$$\langle C_{sv} \rangle = \langle -c_{s,1} \dots -c_{s,2} \rangle \quad (52)$$

$$\langle C_{sq} \rangle = \langle -c_{s,1}L_1 \dots c_{s,2}L_2 \rangle \quad (53)$$

$$[C_w] = \begin{bmatrix} c_{1,1}^w & \dots & c_{1,n}^w & \dots & c_{1,N_m}^w \\ c_{2,1}^w & \dots & c_{2,n}^w & \dots & c_{2,N_m}^w \end{bmatrix} \quad (54)$$

with $c_{i,n}^w = -c_{w,i}W_n(x_i(t))\chi_i$.

$$[\bar{C}_w] = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{c}_{1,1}^w & \bar{c}_{1,2}^w \\ \bar{c}_{2,1}^w & \bar{c}_{2,2}^w \end{bmatrix} \quad (55)$$

with $c_{i,j}^w = -c_{w,i}Z(x_i(t), x_j(t))\chi_i$.

$K =$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Omega_{N_m \times N_m}^2 & [0] & \{K_v\} & \{K_\varphi\} & [K_s]_{N_m \times 2} \\ [0] & \bar{\Omega}_{2 \times 2}^2 & \{\bar{K}_v\} & \{\bar{K}_\varphi\} & [\bar{K}_s]_{2 \times 2} \\ (0) & (0) & \sum_{i=1}^2 k_{s,i} & k_{s,1}L_1 - k_{s,2}L_2 & \langle K_{sp} \rangle \\ (0) & (0) & k_{s,1}L_1 - k_{s,2}L_2 & \sum_{i=1}^2 k_{s,i}L_i^2 & \langle K_{sq} \rangle \\ [K_w]_{2 \times N_m} & [\bar{K}_w]_{2 \times 2} & \langle K_{sp} \rangle^T & \langle K_{sq} \rangle^T & diag[k_{s,i} + k_{w,i}]_{2 \times 2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (56)$$

$$[K_w] = \begin{bmatrix} k_{1,1}^w & \dots & k_{1,n}^w & \dots & k_{1,N_m}^w \\ k_{2,1}^w & \dots & k_{2,n}^w & \dots & k_{2,N_m}^w \end{bmatrix} \quad (57)$$

with $k_{i,n}^w = -k_{w,i}W_n(x_i(t))\chi_i - c_{w,i}\dot{x}_i(t)W'_n(x_i(t))\chi_i$.

$$[\bar{K}_w] = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{k}_{1,1}^w & \bar{k}_{1,2}^w \\ \bar{k}_{2,1}^w & \bar{k}_{2,2}^w \end{bmatrix} \quad (58)$$

with:

$$\bar{k}_{i,j}^w = -k_{w,i}Z(x_i(t), x_j(t))\chi_i - c_{w,i}\dot{x}_i(t)Z'(x_i(t), x_j(t))\chi_i$$

The submatrices $[K]$ have a similar form as the submatrices $[C]$ and can be obtained by replacing the damping coefficient with the stiffness coefficient.

$$P = \begin{Bmatrix} \{F\} \\ \{\bar{F}_a\} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \{\bar{F}_w\} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad \{F\} = \begin{Bmatrix} f_1 \\ \dots \\ f_n \\ \dots \\ f_{N_m} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (59)$$

$$\text{with } f_n = \sum_{i=1}^2 (m_{w,i} + r_i m_c) g W_n(x_i(t)) \chi_i \quad (60)$$

$$\{\bar{F}_a\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \bar{f}_{a,1} \\ \bar{f}_{a,2} \end{Bmatrix} \text{ with } \bar{f}_{a,i} = (m_{w,i} + r_i m_c) g \bar{\omega}_i^2 \chi_i \quad (61)$$

$$\{\bar{F}_w\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \bar{f}_{w,1} \\ \bar{f}_{w,2} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (62)$$

$$\text{with } \bar{f}_{w,i} = c_{w,i} \dot{x}_i(t) \lambda'(x_i(t)) + k_{w,i} \lambda(x_i(t)).$$

Since the positions of excitation caused by the wheels depend on the vehicle velocity and the time increment, (41) must be modified and updated after each time step. It can be solved by direct time integration to obtain the dynamic responses of the system simultaneously.

III. EVALUATION OF BENDING MOMENT AND SHEAR FORCE

Once (41) is solved, the problem of calculating the bending moment and shear force of the beam can be evaluated by differentiating (10) or (22) for the spatial coordinate x . In the case of homogeneous and uniform Euler-Bernoulli beam, the bending moment and shear force are given by:

$$M(x, t) = -EIW_b''(x, t) \quad (63)$$

$$Q(x, t) = -EIW_b'''(x, t) \quad (64)$$

Using (10), the bending moment and shear force based on MDM are given by:

$$M_{MDM}(x, t) = -EIW''(x)^T T(t) \quad (65)$$

$$Q_{MDM}(x, t) = -EIW'''(x)^T T(t) \quad (66)$$

Using (22) and (25), the bending moment and shear force are given by:

$$M_{DyMAM}(x, t) = -EIW''(x)^T T(t) - EI[G''(x, x(t))^T - W''(x)^T \Omega^{-2} W_L(x(t))] XH(t) \quad (67)$$

$$Q_{DyMAM}(x, t) = -EIW'''(x)^T T(t) - EI[G'''(x, x(t))^T - W'''(x)^T \Omega^{-2} W_L(x(t))] XH(t) \quad (68)$$

where $G''(x, x(t))$ and $G'''(x, x(t))$ are the vector of order 2 listing the partial derivative of the static Green's function

$G(x, x_i(t))$, and $W''(x), W'''(x)$ are the vectors of order N_m listing the normal vibration modes $W_n(x)$ with respect to x .

IV. NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

The applicability of DyMAM in the VBI analysis validation was conducted based on numerical examples. The proposed algorithms were implemented in the MATLAB environment [23]. Without loss of generality, let us consider a single span simply supported beam. The natural circular frequencies of the beam are calculated by the solution of the eigenvalue for free vibration is:

$$\omega_n = \left(\frac{n\pi}{L}\right)^2 \sqrt{\frac{EI}{\mu}}$$

and the modal shape [24]:

$$W_{b,n}(x) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\mu L}} \sin\left(\frac{n\pi x}{L}\right).$$

According to (5.8) in [24], the static Green's function of the simply supported beam is given by:

$$G(x, x_i(t)) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{6EI} [-(L - x_i(t))x^2 + (2L^2 - 3Lx_i(t) + x_i^2(t))x_i(t)]x & \text{for } x \leq x_i(t) \\ \frac{1}{6EI} [-(L - x)x_i^2(t) + (2L^2 - 3Lx + x^2)x]x_i(t) & \text{for } x \geq x_i(t) \end{cases} \quad (69)$$

The following mechanical parameters were chosen for the beam and the vehicle: span length $L=40$ m, mass per unit length $\mu=12 \times 10^3$ kg/m, flexural rigidity $EI=12.75 \times 10^{10}$ Nm², and the damping ratios of the beam were set to be $\zeta=0.02$, vehicle body mass $m_c=36000$ kg, mass moment of inertia $J_c=1.44 \times 10^5$ kgm², axle mass $m_{w,1}=m_{w,2}=2000$ kg, suspension stiffness $k_{s,1}=k_{s,2}=9 \times 10^6$ N/m, suspension damping $c_{s,1}=c_{s,2}=72 \times 10^3$ Ns/m, tire stiffness $k_{w,1}=k_{w,2}=36 \times 10^6$ N/m, $c_{w,1}=c_{w,2}=72 \times 10^3$ Ns/m, axle distance $L_1=L_2=1$ m, and velocity $V=10$ m/s. It was assumed that the front axle of the vehicle enters the beam at the instant $t=0$ s.

The surface irregularity was assumed in the form of a harmonic function represented by:

$$\lambda(x) = \left(\frac{d_r}{2}\right) \left[1 - \cos\left(\frac{2\pi x}{l_r}\right)\right] \quad (70)$$

where d_r and l_r are the surface irregularity depth and length, respectively. The value of two ratios was adopted as:

$$\frac{48EI d_r}{(m_c + \sum m_i) g L^3} = 0.05, \quad \frac{L}{l_r} = 10.$$

Equation (41) was solved using the Newmark- β method, with the coefficients $\beta=1/6$ and $\gamma=1/2$. The time step was chosen as $\Delta t=0.0001$ s. For comparison, the numerical analytical result of the DyMAM procedure was compared with the results evaluated by MDM and MAM [20]. The first five modes of vibration were retained in the analysis and the Newmark- β integral method was used to find dynamic responses in all approaches. Figures 2 and 3 show the time histories of the vertical displacement of the vehicle body and the displacement at the mid-span of the beam based on the considered approaches. Furthermore, Figures 4 and 5 show the bending moment and the shear force distribution at $t=2$ s.. Overall, a good agreement was obtained from the results.

Fig. 2. Vertical displacement of vehicle body versus time.

Fig. 3. Vertical displacement at mid-span of the beam versus time.

Fig. 4. Bending moment distributions along the beam at the instant $t=2$ s.

Fig. 5. Shear force distribution along the beam at the instant $t=2$ s.

Figure 2 illustrates that the solid line coincides with the dotted line, which means that the vertical displacement of the vehicle body determined by the DyMAM approach was the same as the one given by the MDM solution. Figure 3 shows the displacement in the mid-span of the beam. The solid line was very close to the dashed line, but there was a slight

deviation between them. The cause of this was that the response of the beam in MAM was evaluated as the sum of the MDM and the quasi-static response, which considers the quasi-static displacements of the beam under the quasi-static interaction forces transmitted by the moving vehicle associated with the truncated higher-order eigenfunctions [20]. DyMAM agrees with both MDM and MAM in calculating the dynamic response of the beam. The shortcoming of the two methods is that MDM does not consider the influence of the quasistatic effect and MAM neglects the inertial and damping effects of the vehicle.

Figure 4 shows the bending moment distribution along the beam calculated at $t=2$ s. It can be seen that the DyMAM approach converged with the MAM. Figure 5 shows the shear force distributions of the beam at $t=2$ s. It can be easily seen that the difference in the convergence of the two correction methods is quite considerable. In particular, the differences at the two jump locations and the segment between them are the most pronounced. With a speed of 10 m/s, at $t=2$ s, the axles move 20 m, which means that the front axle of the vehicle is in the middle of the beam while the rear axle is 2m to the left.

As shown in Figures 4 and 5, at positions $x_1=20$ m and $x_2=18$ m, MDM was unable to capture any discontinuities in the bending moment and shear force. Meanwhile, there were two points of discontinuity captured by the MAM and the DyMAM approaches with different levels of accuracy. Two points of discontinuity appear since the two-axle vehicle model was employed and the whole vehicle stood on the beam at that time. On the other hand, the jumps in the shear force can be clearly observed when applying MAM and DyMAM. As shown in Figure 4, the jumps occur at two points and divide the shear force distribution into three segments. In the case of MAM, there was no change in each of these segments. However, in the case of DyMAM, each segment showed a change in the nonlinear form. This phenomenon can be explained by the dynamic effect of the vehicle: MAM only considers gravitational effects and excludes damping and inertial effects induced by the motion of the moving vehicle. Meanwhile, the inertial, damping, and gravitational effects resulting from the moving vehicle are included in DyMAM. Furthermore, the pitching effect also contributes to the dynamic response of the beam, further complicating things.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study formulated the motion equations of a beam subjected to a moving vehicle in matrix form, based on the dynamic modal acceleration method, and validated them through a numerical example. The quasistatic effect of the beam transmitted by the moving vehicle associated with the contribution of high modes was considered. The DyMAM correction was used for the first time in VBI analysis. This approach has some advantageous features compared to the previous modal correction methods, as follows:

- The dynamic response of the beam and vehicle can be calculated directly by using a step-by-step integration procedure, as it supplies an adequate approximation in calculating the response of the beam in VBI analysis.

- The method can consider both actions of gravitational, damping, and inertial effects due to the moving vehicle.
- The performances of DyMAM can capture the discontinuities in the bending moment and shear force and the jump in the shear force.

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REFERENCES

- [1] H. T. Duy, N. D. Diem, G. V. Tan, V. V. Hiep, and N. V. Thuan, "Stochastic Higher-order Finite Element Model for the Free Vibration of a Continuous Beam resting on Elastic Support with Uncertain Elastic Modulus," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 9985–9990, Feb. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5456>.
- [2] P. C. Nguyen, "Nonlinear Inelastic Earthquake Analysis of 2D Steel Frames," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 6393–6398, Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3855>.
- [3] T. D. Hien, N. D. Hung, N. T. Hiep, G. V. Tan, and N. V. Thuan, "Finite Element Analysis of a Continuous Sandwich Beam resting on Elastic Support and Subjected to Two Degree of Freedom Sprung Vehicles," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 10310–10315, Apr. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5464>.
- [4] T. D. Hien, N. D. Hung, N. T. Kien, and H. C. Noh, "The variability of dynamic responses of beams resting on elastic foundation subjected to vehicle with random system parameters," *Applied Mathematical Modelling*, vol. 67, pp. 676–687, Mar. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apm.2018.11.018>.
- [5] J. P. Yang, "Theoretical Formulation of Amplifier–Vehicle–Bridge System Based on Sophisticated Vehicle Model," *Journal of Vibration Engineering & Technologies*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 789–794, Feb. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42417-021-00409-4>.
- [6] L. Ding, H. Hao, and X. Zhu, "Evaluation of dynamic vehicle axle loads on bridges with different surface conditions," *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, vol. 323, no. 3, pp. 826–848, Jun. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsv.2009.01.051>.
- [7] E. Esmailzadeh and N. Jalili, "Vehicle–passenger–structure interaction of uniform bridges traversed by moving vehicles," *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, vol. 260, no. 4, pp. 611–635, Feb. 2003, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-460X\(02\)00960-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-460X(02)00960-4).
- [8] P. Lou, "Vertical dynamic responses of a simply supported bridge subjected to a moving train with two-wheelset vehicles using modal analysis method," *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, vol. 64, no. 9, pp. 1207–1235, 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1002/nme.1426>.
- [9] S. S. Law and X. Q. Zhu, "Bridge dynamic responses due to road surface roughness and braking of vehicle," *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, vol. 282, no. 3, pp. 805–830, Apr. 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsv.2004.03.032>.
- [10] J. P. Yang, "Theoretical Formulation of Three-Mass Vehicle Model for Vehicle–Bridge Interaction," *International Journal of Structural Stability and Dynamics*, vol. 21, no. 07, Jul. 2021, Art. no. 2171004, <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0219455421710048>.
- [11] H. L. Soriano and F. V. Filho, "On the modal acceleration method in structural dynamics. Mode truncation and static correction," *Computers & Structures*, vol. 29, no. 5, pp. 777–782, Jan. 1988, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0045-7949\(88\)90345-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0045-7949(88)90345-8).
- [12] P. Leger and E. L. Wilson, "Modal summation methods for structural dynamic computations," *Earthquake Engineering & Structural Dynamics*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 23–27, 1988, <https://doi.org/10.1002/eqe.4290160103>.
- [13] G. Borino and G. Muscolino, "Mode-superposition methods in dynamic analysis of classically and non-classically damped linear systems," *Earthquake Engineering & Structural Dynamics*, vol. 14, no. 5, pp. 705–717, 1986, <https://doi.org/10.1002/eqe.4290140503>.
- [14] A. D'Avèni and G. Muscolino, "Improved dynamic correction method in seismic analysis of both classically and non-classically damped structures," *Earthquake Engineering & Structural Dynamics*, vol. 30, no. 4, pp. 501–517, 2001, <https://doi.org/10.1002/eqe.20>.
- [15] C. J. Camarda, R. T. Haftka, and M. F. Riley, "An evaluation of higher-order modal methods for calculating transient structural response," *Computers & Structures*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 89–101, Jan. 1987, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0045-7949\(87\)90184-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0045-7949(87)90184-2).
- [16] M. A. Akgün, "A New Family Of Mode-Superposition Methods For Response Calculations," *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, vol. 167, no. 2, pp. 289–302, Oct. 1993, <https://doi.org/10.1006/jsvi.1993.1336>.
- [17] A. V. Pesterev and L. A. Bergman, "An Improved Series Expansion of the Solution to the Moving Oscillator Problem," *Journal of Vibration and Acoustics*, vol. 122, no. 1, pp. 54–61, Jan. 1999, <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.568436>.
- [18] A. V. Pesterev, B. Yang, L. A. Bergman, and C.-A. Tan, "Response of Elastic Continuum Carrying Multiple Moving Oscillators," *Journal of Engineering Mechanics*, vol. 127, no. 3, pp. 260–265, Mar. 2001, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9399\(2001\)127:3\(260\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9399(2001)127:3(260)).
- [19] B. Biondi, G. Muscolino, and A. Sidoti, "Methods for Calculating Bending Moment and Shear Force in the Moving Mass Problem," *Journal of Vibration and Acoustics*, vol. 126, no. 4, pp. 542–552, Dec. 2004, <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.1804992>.
- [20] B. Biondi and G. Muscolino, "New improved series expansion for solving the moving oscillator problem," *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, vol. 281, no. 1, pp. 99–117, Mar. 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsv.2004.01.018>.
- [21] C. Bilello, M. Di Paola, and S. Salamone, "A correction method for the analysis of continuous linear one-dimensional systems under moving loads," *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, vol. 315, no. 1, pp. 226–238, Aug. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsv.2008.01.040>.
- [22] A. Palmeri and M. Lombardo, "A new modal correction method for linear structures subjected to deterministic and random loadings," *Computers & Structures*, vol. 89, no. 11, pp. 844–854, Jun. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruc.2011.02.020>.
- [23] "MathWorks." [Online]. Available: <https://www.mathworks.com/>.
- [24] L. Frýba, *Vibration of Solids and Structures Under Moving Loads*. Prague, Czech Republic: Thomas Telford, 1999.

Analyzing the Impact of Fly Ash Additive Ratio on Lubricant Properties

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ABSTRACT

Preventing surface damage is crucial for optimal machine performance, with lubricants and additives playing a vital role in achieving this objective. This study specifically focuses on evaluating the influence of fly-ash additives on the wear resistance of machine components when incorporated into lubricant oil. The experiments were conducted following ASTM standard operating conditions, utilizing the four-ball wear test to measure the scratch width and weight loss of balls using different lubricant oil formulations, including 0, 0.1%, 0.5%, 0.75%, and 1% additive. The findings demonstrate that the inclusion of 0.5% fly ash additive in the lubricant oil results in a significant reduction in both scratch width and weight loss of the balls. However, it should be noted that higher additive ratios may lead to increased scratch width and weight loss due to the agglomeration of the fly ash particles on the sliding surfaces. To achieve optimal effectiveness in reducing friction and wear, it is recommended to carefully control the content of fly ash within an appropriate range. Furthermore, this study highlights the width of scratches on balls as a reliable indicator for assessing the anti-wear properties of oils. The insights gained from this research offer valuable guidance to manufacturers in the selection of suitable anti-wear oils for specific applications. Further investigations could explore the impact of different lubricants and additive ratios to identify the most appropriate lubrication parameters. Overall, this study contributes to a better understanding of the effects of fly ash additives on the performance of lubricant oil and provides practical guidance for optimizing lubrication strategies in diverse industrial contexts.

Keywords-fly ash additive; lubricant; wear resistance; scratch width; scratch diameter

I. INTRODUCTION

Industrial lubricants are in high demand and typically require an appropriate additive in a specified ratio. Among the most critical quality criteria for lubricants is the viscosity index which measures their thermal stability. In order to enhance the load-carrying capacity and other lubrication properties, lubricant manufacturers have proposed a variety of additive packages. The lubricating properties of lubricants when using nano Al_2O_3 particles as additives were studied in [1, 2]. The addition of additives to lubricants may improve their rheological properties. Moreover, nano Al_2O_3 can also improve the heat resistance by reducing the viscosity at high temperatures. The dynamic viscosity and rheological properties of the oil-nano Al_2O_3 mixture have been examined at various additive ratios and temperatures. In addition, there have been various studies on the influence of particulate additives on lubricating oil quality. Some researchers have conducted studies on the effect of different ratios of metal oxides, such as CuO , Fe_2O_3 , NiO , and Al_2O_3 , in lubricants, and the influence of temperature on oil viscosity. Authors in [3] studied the influence of CuO , Fe_2O_3 , and NiO nano-particles and temperature on oil viscosity. Various ratios of nano metal oxides at different temperatures were considered. The findings demonstrated that the viscosity of the oil mixture was influenced by these factors, depending on the ratio of the additives. Authors in [4] reported that the viscosity of heavy oil mixtures can decrease by 20-93% depending on the proportion of emulsion solution blended into the lubricating oil. Authors in [5] reported that the viscosity reduction relies on the size and density of the metal particles. Authors in [6] found that SiO_2 nanoparticles can reduce friction by acting as rolling elements at the friction interface. Authors in [7] developed a special oil with improved lubricity by adding SiO_2 nanoparticles, resulting in improved thermo-physical properties and tribological performance. Authors in [8] investigated the use of composite nanoparticles synthesized by chemical deposition as new additives in grease, which reduce the friction coefficient and wear scratch diameter significantly when added at a 1 wt% concentration and form a solid-liquid phase composite lubricating film. Authors in [9] conducted a comparison of the tribological properties between chemically modified rapeseed oil and two distinct anti-wear nano additives, TiO_2 and Al_2O_3 , using a pin-on-disc tribometer, and found that TiO_2 shows better friction properties than the oil with fibrous nano Al_2O_3 wire [9]. Authors in [10] investigated the effect of adding ZnO to rapeseed oil at different concentrations on a four-ball machine and observed a reduction of the wear rate with an addition of 1%wt ZnO , although the friction coefficient remained unchanged. Authors in [11] studied the impact of CaCO_3 and SiO_2 particles on the properties of lithium-based grease, and found that the additives improved the properties of the original grease. Authors in [12] reported that the use of CuO and TiO_2 nanoparticles to a metal-working polymeric lubricant resulted in a significant improvement in anti-wear properties, with 0.01 wt.% TiO_2 and 0.05 wt.% CuO showing the highest improvement of 77% and 33%, respectively, proving the potential of nano lubricants in enhancing mechanical component efficiency. Authors in [13] investigated the properties of CuO particles in lubricant and observed a

60.83% decrease of wear rate and 33.1% reduction in friction coefficient with 0.75 wt.% additive used. Other studies that have also reported the effect of metal oxide nano additives on the lubricating properties and the decrease in viscosity of certain types of industrial oil due to the presence of these nanoparticles are [14-20]. Research on the rheological properties of multigrade oil mixture mixed with water in the form of vapor or paraffin in solid state has also been published. Accordingly, the viscosity of the oil mixture increases with the addition of paraffin and decreases in the case of an oil-steam mixture [21]. In mechanical machining, the coolant mixture is also supplemented with metal oxide particles to improve the cooling and lubrication performance in cutting and machining processes [22, 23]. Although previous studies have presented that those additives can enhance the lubricating properties of lubricants and extend the operational lifespan of machine components, however, specific investigation regarding the impact of these additives on the load-carrying capacity of the oil has not been conducted. Therefore, investigating the lubrication properties of oil with additives could be a solution to change the viscosity or stabilize the working conditions of machines.

Fly ash is composed of some metal oxides, ranging from nano to micro in size, and is sourced from thermal power plant dust as a byproduct of coal-fired furnaces. Fly ash can be utilized in various fields to enhance the properties of the used mixture [24, 25]. Besides, in the field of lubricating industry, the investigation will focus on determining the optimal concentration of the additive to enhance the lubrication properties of the lubricant, minimize oil residue emissions, and promote sustainable development. Previous studies have demonstrated the potential of additives to enhance the lubricating properties of lubricants and prolong the operational lifespan of machine components. However, a specific investigation into the impact of fly ash additives on the load-carrying capacity of the oil has not yet been published. Therefore, further research is necessary in order to assess the influence of fly ash additives on the load-carrying capacity and anti-wear properties of lubricants. It is essential to determine the optimal concentration of fly ash that can effectively improve the lubrication performance while minimizing the emission of oil residues. By conducting this optimization process, sustainable development can be promoted while mitigating the adverse effects associated with oil refining and the disposal of lubricant waste. One of the aims of this research is to protect the environment by addressing the negative consequences linked to oil refining and the disposal of lubricant waste. To evaluate the load-carrying capacity, thermal stability, and other pertinent characteristics of oils, the scientific community relies on the ASTM D-4172 test standard, which is specifically designed for assessing lubricant anti-wear properties. This standard entails measuring the wear scar diameter of the balls in a four-ball machine, under controlled conditions of temperature, load, and duration of ball contact, reaching a point where the viscosity of the oil can no longer effectively separate the friction surfaces. Adopting this standardized evaluation methodology can provide reliable insights into the performance of lubricants containing fly ash, facilitating comparisons with existing lubricants in the field.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In order to evaluate the specific lubricating properties in accordance with the ASTM D4172 standard, thorough preparation and planning were undertaken for the experimental equipment and test parameters. The stability of the equipment is meticulously verified, and the parameters were subsequently adjusted as outlined below:

- The temperature was kept constant at $75^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$.
- The speed of the upper ball was set to about $1200 \text{ rpm} \pm 60 \text{ rpm}$.
- The experiment time was $60 \text{ min} \pm 1 \text{ min}$.
- The load applied on the upper ball was $392 \text{ N} \pm 2 \text{ N}$.

Figure 1 shows the principal diagram of the four-ball friction testing machine. The predetermined plan is followed to prepare the lubricating oil, utilizing a commonly employed industrial lubricant to assess specific lubrication properties. Furthermore, fly ash was introduced into the oil mixture at concentrations of 0.5%, 0.75%, and 1% to facilitate a comparative analysis of the lubrication properties.

Fig. 1. Principal operation of a four-ball machine.

The experimental procedure involves using four steel balls with a diameter of 12.7 mm. Three of these balls were positioned in contact with each other and were kept fixed, while the fourth ball was placed on top, contacting the three lower balls. The arrangement was submerged in the test oil, and the temperature was carefully controlled and monitored. The applied force F on the upper ball results in pressure being exerted on the lower balls, leading to the generation of a rotational motion perpendicular to the plane formed by the lower balls. The time of the test was set at 60 min, and once the test was completed, the balls were cleaned and the scratches were measured for further analysis.

The experimental procedure includes the following steps: (1) Clean the balls and prepare the oil cup for each experiment. After cleaning, all parts should be handled with new wiping cloths. There should be no residue of the solvent when the test oil is replenished, and the apparatus is assembled. (2) Put one of the clean balls onto the spindle of the machine and verify its tightness. (3) Assemble three of the other cleaned balls into the test oil cup and tighten the holding mechanism for the lower balls. (4) Pour the oil or oil mixture under evaluation into the test oil cup. (5) Install the oil cup onto the machine and avoid shock loading by gradually applying the test load. (6) Control

the temperature of the oil or the oil mixture at the required value. (7) Once the desired temperature is reached, turn on the power to transfer the motion for the upper ball. (8) After the experiment is completed, remove the oil cup and clean the balls. (9) Measure the scratch dimensions on the balls using a highly accurate measuring device after they are cleaned.

A. Experimental Balls

The experimental balls were meticulously prepared to ensure the experiment's accuracy. A suitable quantity of balls was carefully cleaned and examined for diameter and surface hardness prior to their installation in the machine. Following each experiment, the balls underwent thorough cleaning, were marked for identification, and were categorized.

B. Experimental Oil

The main technical specifications of the experimental oil are listed in Table I.

TABLE I. MAIN TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS OF THE EXPERIMENTAL OIL

Specification	Test method	Unit	Value
Specific gravity at 15°C	ASTM D4052	g/ml	0.868
Kinematic viscosity at 100°C	ASTM D445	mm ² /s	14.6
Kinematic viscosity at 40°C	ASTM D445	mm ² /s	126
Viscosity index	ASTM D2270	-	117
Cleveland flash point	ASTM D92	°C	205
Sulfated Ash	ASTM D874	%	0.88

The viscosity of the lubricating oil significantly impacts its lubrication quality, as indicated by the scratch test conducted in accordance with the ASTM D4172 standard. However, relying solely on the viscosity index for evaluating the lubrication characteristics may be misleading since the properties of the oil additives also play a significant role. In low-temperature environments, the viscosity of the oil increases, causing difficulties in the starting equipment due to the direct frictional surface. To address this issue, special additive compounds were added to the lubricating oil to reduce its viscosity dependence on environment temperature, resulting in multi-grade oil. This oil provides lubrication while enabling the engine to start smoothly in low temperatures. However, the viscosity index is not the only parameter affecting the quality of lubrication, as the properties of oil additives also play a significant role, as indicated in the specifications provided by the supplier.

C. Fly Ash Additive

The use of fly ash in this study as an additive for lubricant was explored due to components such as metal oxide particles of SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 , K_2O , Fe_2O_3 , among others. These components have a spherical structure and a micrometer-sized particle, making them a suitable friction modifier to increase viscosity and thermal conductivity of lubricant oil mixtures, while also extending their service life and reducing sludge deposition. For this study, fly ash from a thermal power plant was chosen as an inert additive at 0.5%, 0.75%, and 1% ratios to the selected oil. The determined optimal concentration enhanced wear resistance, reduced sludge emissions, promoting environmentally sustainable development and minimizing the environmental impacts of oil refining. The main components of fly ash used in the current study are shown in Table II.

TABLE II. COMPONENTS OF FLY-ASH ADDITIVE

Component	Percentage
SiO ₂	57.02%
Al ₂ O ₃	23.82%
K ₂ O	6.56%
Fe ₂ O ₃	4.69%

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To evaluate the influence of fly ash content percentage on the lubricating properties of industrial oil, especially the anti-wear ability of the oil blend, the weight of the balls before and after the experiments was carefully measured. Additionally, a microscope measuring device was used to measure the scratch sizes on the balls during the experiments. In each experiment, the scratch diameter of the ball was measured and processed for further analysis. The parameters of the balls before and after the experiment are the average values of these parameters for each experiment.

Experiments were carried out with oil and three different ratios of additives, and the scratches on the upper and lower balls with and without additives were observed. Figures 2-5 show the images of the scratches on the upper and lower balls for these experiments. The wear resistance of the material with and without the additive was assessed by measuring the width of the scratch on the upper ball and the diameter of the scratch on the lower ball, compared to the case without the additive. For the upper ball, a long scratch resulting from the friction between the upper and lower balls was observed, as illustrated in Figure 2(a), Figure 3(a), Figure 4(a), and Figure 5(a) corresponding to additive contents of 0%, 0.5%, 0.75%, and 1%, respectively. For the lower ball, the wear mark had a circular shape that could be easily observed and measured with the scratch diameter, as illustrated in Figure 2(b), Figure 3(b), Figure 4(b), and Figure 5(b) correspond to additive contents of 0%, 0.5%, 0.75%, and 1%, respectively. Additionally, the mass of the balls before and after the experiment was measured for further analysis and evaluation.

Fig. 2. Surface of balls experimented with oil without additive. (a) Upper ball, (b) lower ball.

Fig. 3. Surface captured of balls experimented with oil and 0.5% additive. (a) Upper ball, (b) lower ball.

Fig. 4. Surface captured of balls experimented with oil and 0.75% additive. (a) Upper ball, (b) lower ball.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5. Surface captured of balls experimented with oil and 175% additive. (a) Upper ball, (b) lower ball.

TABLE III. AVERAGE BALL WEIGHT

Fly-ash additive	Before the experiments (g)	Standard deviation	After the experiments (g)	Standard deviation
0%	8.328	0.0021	8.327	0.0019
0.5%	8.336	0.0014	8.335	0.0014
0.75%	8.350	0.0015	8.348	0.0014
1%	8.345	0.0012	8.343	0.0005

Fig. 6. Average ball weight.

TABLE IV. AVERAGE BALL SCRATCH DIAMETER

Fly-ash additive	Average ball scratch diameter (mm)	Standard deviation
0%	0.426	0.017
0.5%	0.417	0.004
0.75%	0.495	0.007
1%	0.503	0.012

Table III presents the average of ball's mass and their standard deviation before and after the experiment. Figure 6 provides a visual representation of the wear resistance of the lubricating oil or lubricating oil mixtures with 0.5%, 0.75%, and 1% fly ash additive. After a certain working time, the balls

experience corrosion, reflected by a decrease in mass. It can be seen that both cases with or without additive using in the oil, resulted in a weight loss of approximately 0.001-0.002 g. In the majority of the experiments, the observed average mass reduction was 0.001 g, except when involving 0.75% and 1% fly ash additives, where each ball experienced an average mass decrease of 0.002 g. This finding suggests that the inclusion of fly ash positively influences the wear resistance of lubricating oils. However, it is crucial to limit the ratio of the additive in the oil to 0.5%. This limitation could be ascribed to the additive's function of converting wet into wet-rolling friction by incorporating metal oxide particles between the machine component surfaces. Additionally, it could contribute to a more even corrosion of the friction surfaces. If the additive ratio is higher, the metal oxide particles, even in small sizes, may affect the friction performance by falling into the abrasive wear area. These observations provide insight into the potential applications of fly ash as an additive in lubricating oils. Furthermore, the scratch diameter of the balls was measured, and the resulting mean value and standard deviation are indicated in Table IV. These measurements are also visualized in Figure 7. Similarly, for the upper balls, the scratch width was determined, and the mean value and standard deviation were computed and are listed in Table V, and illustrated in Figure 8.

Fig. 7. Average diameter of ball scratch depending on additive content.

Fig. 8. Average width of ball scratch depending on additive content.

TABLE V. AVERAGE BALL SCRATCH WIDTH

Fly-ash additive	Average ball scratch width (mm)	Standard deviation
0%	0.753	0.011
0.5%	0.643	0.011
0.75%	0.667	0.014
1%	0.701	0.015

The average diameter of ball scratch with different fly-ash additive contents is shown in Figure 7. The results indicate that the average scratch diameter decreases with the increase in the amount of the additive. The scratch diameters for balls without any additive and with 0.5% additive were 0.426 mm and 0.417 mm, respectively. However, the addition of 0.75% and 1% fly-ash resulted in an increase in the scratch diameter to 0.495 mm and 0.503 mm, respectively. The standard deviation values for all the cases were relatively small, ranging from 0.004 to 0.017, suggesting that the results are consistent and reliable. These findings suggest that the addition of an appropriate amount of fly-ash has the potential to enhance the wear resistance of the surface of machine components, as indicated by the decrease in scratch diameter. However, excessive amounts of the additive may lead to a reverse effect, as observed in the 0.75% and 1% cases. This may be due to the mechanism of action of the fly-ash additive and its impact on frictional properties. When the fly-ash additive is added to the lubricant, the metal oxide particles in the additive fill the gaps between the frictional surfaces and form a protective film, minimizing friction between the surfaces. Therefore, with the addition of the additive, the scratch on the ball surface is smaller compared to the case without the additive. However, when the amount of fly-ash is increased beyond a certain level, the metal oxide particles concentrate too much and cannot be uniformly dispersed on the frictional surface, resulting in wear and tear of the surface. Thus, the amount of additive needs to be precisely controlled to ensure maximum effectiveness in reducing friction and wear.

The current literature lacks studies that investigate the influence of fly-ash additive ratios on the corrosion resistance properties of oil mixtures. In this study, the aim was to fill this research gap by investigating the scratch width of balls treated with various concentrations of fly-ash additive. The results shown in Table V indicate a decrease in scratch width as the fly-ash additive content increases up to 0.5%, followed by a slight increase at higher additive ratios. This observed trend can be attributed to the ability of fly-ash particles to fill the gaps between sliding surfaces, thereby creating a protective layer that effectively reduces friction and minimizes material removal during scratching, ultimately resulting in reduced scratch width. However, at higher fly-ash additive ratios, particle clustering and uneven dispersion on the sliding surface occurred. This phenomenon resulted in irregular wear patterns and an increase in scratch width. This observation is supported by the slightly higher scratch width values recorded at 0.75% and 1% additive content. The low standard deviation values indicate that the scratch width measurements are consistent and reproducible.

Based on the findings, we can conclude that an optimal fly-ash additive content of 0.5% is favorable for reducing scratch width and improving the frictional properties of the sliding

surfaces. This optimal content level enables the formation of a protective layer, which effectively reduces friction and wear. However, it is crucial to control the fly-ash additive content within an appropriate range since exceeding this threshold may lead to particle agglomeration and the formation of abrasive regions, consequently increasing the wear rate. Thus, achieving maximum effectiveness in reducing friction and wear requires careful control of the fly-ash additive content. Additionally, it is important to note that the scratch width measurements and standard deviations for the ball bearing component vary depending on the additive content. This further emphasizes the need for comparative studies and examination of the effects of additive content on lubrication performance.

In summary, the addition of additives at an appropriate ratio has been shown to enhance oil viscosity, leading to the formation of a protective lubricant layer on the surface of machine parts. This layer effectively prevents wear and reduces oil consumption during machine operation. However, it should be noted that excessively high viscosity can have a negative impact on lubrication, resulting in decreased wear reduction. Furthermore, the incorporation of minute metal oxide particles in the additives facilitates the conversion of sliding friction to rolling friction between machine components, resulting in decreased friction and wear during operation.

However, it is essential to acknowledge the limitations of this study. There are additional known factors that can impact the overall performance of the lubricant, such as the friction coefficient, wear rate, and surface roughness. These factors could be further studied to conduct more comprehensive research. Furthermore, it is important to note that the current study was conducted under controlled laboratory conditions. The lubricating performance may be influenced differently under real-world operating conditions, where factors such as varying temperatures, different load conditions, and continuous usage come into play. Therefore, conducting experiments under more realistic conditions would provide a more accurate evaluation of the additive's effectiveness. Future studies will focus on examining various additive ratios for different lubricant types to determine optimal lubrication parameters. Moreover, a more comprehensive investigation of the rheological properties of the oil mixture with fly-ash additives will be conducted. These endeavors aim to further optimize the lubrication performance and provide valuable insights for industrial applications.

IV. CONCLUSION

The objective of the current study was to assess the impact of fly ash additive on lubricant oil in reducing friction and minimizing wear on machine components. The results demonstrated that the inclusion of a 0.5% concentration of fly ash additive in the lubricant oil resulted in the smallest scratch width and the lowest weight loss of the balls. However, at higher additive ratios, there was a slight increase in scratch width and weight loss due to the agglomeration of fly-ash particles on the sliding surfaces. It is recommended to maintain the appropriate range of fly-ash additive content for maximum effectiveness. Further research can explore different types of lubricants and additive ratios to identify the most suitable lubrication parameters. The study emphasizes the importance

of choosing the right additive concentration to ensure the performance and service life of machine components. The addition of fly ash additive to the oil has been found to improve its anti-wear properties by converting wet into wet-rolling friction and introducing metal oxide particles between the surfaces of machine components. The study concludes that an optimal concentration of 0.5% fly ash enhances the anti-wear properties while preserving the essential physical and chemical properties of the oil. This information is valuable for manufacturers in making informed decisions regarding the selection and formulation of lubricating oils with improved anti-wear capabilities.

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REFERENCES

- [1] T.-A. Bui, V.-H. Pham, N.-T. Bui, and A. Nguyen, "Effect of Al₂O₃ Nanoparticle on Rheological Properties of Oil," *International Journal of Mechanical and Production Engineering Research and Development*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 2911–2918, Sep. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.24247/ijmperdjun2020276>.
- [2] T. A. Bui, D. D. Le, V. H. Pham, M. T. Nguyen, and N. T. Bui, "A Study of Al₂O₃ Nanoparticle Effect on Lubricant to Hydrodynamic Journal Bearing," *International Journal of Mechanical and Production Engineering Research and Development*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 3607–3618, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.24247/ijmperdjun2020342>.
- [3] H. Patel, S. Shah, R. Ahmed, and S. Ucan, "Effects of nanoparticles and temperature on heavy oil viscosity," *Journal of Petroleum Science and Engineering*, vol. 167, pp. 819–828, Aug. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.petrol.2018.04.069>.
- [4] H. Patel, "Effect of Nanoparticles and Solvent Based Emulsion on Heavy Oil Viscosity," M. S. thesis, University of Oklahoma, Norman, OK, USA, 2016.
- [5] Y. H. Shokrlu and T. Babadagli, "Viscosity reduction of heavy oil/bitumen using micro- and nano-metal particles during aqueous and non-aqueous thermal applications," *Journal of Petroleum Science and Engineering*, vol. 119, pp. 210–220, Jul. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.petrol.2014.05.012>.
- [6] Y. Shen *et al.*, "Synergistic friction-reduction and wear-resistance mechanism of 3D graphene and SiO₂ nanoblend at harsh friction interface," *Wear*, vol. 488–489, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 204175, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wear.2021.204175>.
- [7] Y. Singh, E. A. Rahim, N. K. Singh, A. Sharma, A. Singla, and A. Palamanit, "Friction and wear characteristics of chemically modified mahua (*madhuca indica*) oil based lubricant with SiO₂ nanoparticles as additives," *Wear*, vol. 508–509, Nov. 2022, Art. no. 204463, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wear.2022.204463>.
- [8] C. Wu, S. Li, Y. Chen, L. Yao, X. Li, and J. Ni, "Tribological properties of chemical composite and physical mixture of ZnO and SiO₂ nanoparticles as grease additives," *Applied Surface Science*, vol. 612, Mar. 2023, Art. no. 155932, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2022.155932>.
- [9] S. Arumugam, S. Baskar, S. Sankaranarayanan, S. H. Athreya, N. L. Narayanan, and S. S. D. Prasad, "Influence of morphology of anti-wear nano additives on Tribological behavior of Chemically Modified Rapeseed Oil," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 390, no. 1, Apr. 2018, Art. no. 012017, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/390/1/012017>.
- [10] T. F. Ionescu, D. Guglea, C. Georgescu, D. Dima, and L. Deleanu, "Influence of ZnO concentration in rapeseed oil on tribological behavior," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 724, no. 1, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 012045, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/724/1/012045>.

- [11] S. Razavi, S. Sabbaghi, and K. Rasouli, "Comparative investigation of the influence of CaCO₃ and SiO₂ nanoparticles on lithium-based grease: Physical, tribological, and rheological properties," *Inorganic Chemistry Communications*, vol. 142, Aug. 2022, Art. no. 109601, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inoche.2022.109601>.
- [12] L. Pena-Paras *et al.*, "Study on the anti-wear properties of metal-forming lubricants with TiO₂ and CuO nanoparticle additives," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 400, no. 6, Dec. 2018, Art. no. 062022, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/400/6/062022>.
- [13] S. Y. Akl, A. A. Abdel-Rehim, and S. Elsouly, "An Experimental Investigation of Tribological Performance of a Lubricant Using Different Nano Additives," SAE International, Warrendale, PA, SAE Technical Paper 2018-01-0833, Apr. 2018. <https://doi.org/10.4271/2018-01-0833>.
- [14] Y. Hamed Shokrlu and T. Babadagli, "Effects of Nano Sized Metals on Viscosity Reduction of Heavy Oil/Bitumen During Thermal Applications," presented at the Canadian Unconventional Resources and International Petroleum Conference, Calgary, Canada, Oct. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.2118/137540-MS>.
- [15] C. Alberto and C. Paternina Ortiz, "Brief Introduction of effect of size of particles for Dissolution Thermodynamics on Nanoparticles and Its Effect on the Decreasing of Viscosity into Heavy Oil," Oct. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29032.52481>.
- [16] M. Chen, C. Li, G.-R. Li, Y.-L. Chen, and C.-G. Zhou, "In situ preparation of well-dispersed CuO nanocatalysts in heavy oil for catalytic aquathermolysis," *Petroleum Science*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 439–446, Apr. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12182-019-0300-3>.
- [17] N. Taghili, M. Manteghian, and A. Jafari, "Novel preparation of MoO₃/γ-Al₂O₃ nanocatalyst: application in extra-heavy oil visbreaking at atmospheric pressure," *Applied Nanoscience*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 1603–1613, May 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13204-020-01271-8>.
- [18] R. M. Jadhav and J. S. Sangwai, "Interaction of Heavy Crude Oil and Nanoparticles for Heavy Oil Upgrading," in *Nanotechnology for Energy and Environmental Engineering*, L. Ledwani and J. S. Sangwai, Eds. Springer International Publishing, 2020, pp. 231–255, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-33774-2_10.
- [19] M. F. Fakoya, H. Patel, and S. N. Shah, "Nanotechnology: Innovative Applications in the Oil & Gas Industry," *International Journal of Global Advanced Materials & Nanotechnology*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 16–30, 2018.
- [20] T.-A. Bui, V.-H. Pham, D.-T. Nguyen, and N.-T. Bui, "Effectiveness of Lubricants and Fly Ash Additive on Surface Damage Resistance under ASTM Standard Operating Conditions," *Coatings*, vol. 13, no. 5, May 2023, Art. no. 851, <https://doi.org/10.3390/coatings13050851>.
- [21] B. Belahcene, A. Mansri, and A. Benmoussat, "Investigation on the Rheological Behavior of Multigrade Oil under the Effect of Organic and Inorganic Impurities," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 4, no. 6, pp. 711–713, Dec. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.513>.
- [22] N. M. M. Reddy and P. K. Chaganti, "Investigating Optimum SiO₂ Nanolubrication During Turning of AISI 420 SS," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 3822–3825, Feb. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2537>.
- [23] M. F. Abdelkarim, L. S. Nasrat, S. M. Elkhodary, A. M. Soliman, A. M. Hassan, and S. H. Mansour, "Volume Resistivity and Mechanical Behavior of Epoxy Nanocomposite Materials," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 775–780, Apr. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.536>.
- [24] S. A. Chandio, B. A. Memon, M. Oad, F. A. Chandio, and M. U. Memon, "Effect of Fly Ash on the Compressive Strength of Green Concrete," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 5728–5731, Jun. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3499>.
- [25] V. T. Phan and T. H. Nguyen, "The Influence of Fly Ash on the Compressive Strength of Recycled Concrete Utilizing Coarse Aggregates from Demolition Works," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 7107–7110, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4145>.

Improved Whale Optimization Algorithm with Deep Learning-Driven Retinal Fundus Image Grading and Retrieval

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ABSTRACT

Several Deep Learning (DL) and medical image Machine Learning (ML) methods have been investigated for efficient data representations of medical images, such as image classification, Content-Based Image Retrieval (CBIR), and image segmentation. CBIR helps medical professionals make decisions by retrieving similar cases and images from electronic medical image databases. CBIR needs expressive data representations for similar image identification and knowledge discovery in massive medical image databases explored by distinct algorithmic methods. In this study, an Improved Whale Optimization Algorithm with Deep Learning-Driven Retinal Fundus Image Grading and Retrieval (IWOADL-RFIGR) approach was developed. The presented IWOADL-RFIGR method mainly focused on retrieving and classifying retinal fundus images. The proposed IWOADL-RFIGR method used the Bilateral Filtering (BF) method to preprocess the retinal images, a lightweight Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) based on scratch learning with Euclidean distance-based similarity measurement for image retrieval, and the Least Square Support Vector Machine (LS-SVM) model for image classification. Finally, the IWOA was used as a hyperparameter optimization technique to improve overall performance. The experimental validation of the IWOADL-RFIGR model on a benchmark dataset exhibited better performance than other models.

Keywords-retinal fundus images; image retrieval; image classification; deep learning; parameter tuning

I. INTRODUCTION

Data retrieval plays an important role in the evolution of technology in the current technological scenario with several databases [1]. CBIR is one of the most common image retrieval methods, which is applied in various domains, such as military applications, medical image analysis, historical research, and many more. Effective data representation and feature extraction are the main elements of successful medical imaging tasks [2]. Researchers generally adopt medical field knowledge and ask for annotations from medical experts. For example, conventional image processing methods, such as filters or edge detection methods, are used to extract clinically related spatial features from images obtained using distinct image modalities [3]. All significant areas of the internal eye constitute the fundus area, which can be identified just opposite the eye lens. The fundus area contains the posterior pole, fovea, retina, optic disc, macula, and blood vessels present in the eye [4]. An ophthalmoscope is used to analyze the fundus area of the eye. The analysis of the fundus area is performed with the help of a

fundus high-resolution camera [5], which operates on the same principle as the ophthalmoscope. Numerous medical conditions of the eye, such as cotton wool spots, exudates, constrictions and abnormalities in blood vessels, hemorrhages, etc., can be monitored using images acquired from a fundus camera [6].

Over the years, DL has been implemented in several domains, including medical image analysis [7]. DL may recognize features precisely from input data for segmentation or classification and commonly outpaces every conventional image analysis method. DL methods do not need to derive handcrafted features, whereas they needed broad data for training purposes [8]. On the contrary, ML methods need the extraction of handcrafted features but do not require large data for training purposes. In DR recognition, ML methods have to derive the vessel initially, following the DR lesions' extraction factors for classification purposes. DL applications cover image detection, segmentation, retrieval, registration, and classification. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are a commonly used DL method that has a very high potential for image analysis [9]. There is a substantial amount of effort in

automating DR image classification through DL to help eye specialists identify diseases at their initial levels. On the other hand, many of these efforts focus on recognizing DR rather than finding several DR levels [10]. Additionally, limited efforts were made to locate and classify every DR lesion type, which is highly useful in practice as ophthalmologists could assess the severity of DR and observe its development related to the appearance of such lesions.

This study developed the Improved Whale Optimization Algorithm with Deep Learning-Driven Retinal Fundus Image Grading and Retrieval (IWOADL-RFIGR) method. The proposed method used the Bilateral Filtering (BF) approach to preprocess retinal images, lightweight CNN based on scratch learning with Euclidean distance-based similarity measurement for image retrieval, and the Least Square Support Vector Machine (LS-SVM) model for image classification. Finally, the IWOA was used as a hyperparameter optimization method to improve overall performance. The proposed method was experimentally validated on a benchmark dataset.

II. RELATED WORKS

In [11], an optimal deep CNN was developed for RF image classification, using the U-Net approach for image segmentation and allowing the infested area to be properly identified. The EfficientNet feature extraction algorithm was used to create a feature vector. Finally, the Mayfly Optimization with KELM (MFO-KELM) method was executed for classification. In [12], a novel AI with an Optimal DCNN (AI-ODCNN) system was proposed for RFIC, using Gaussian blur noise removal and CLAHE-based contrast advancement to preprocess the RFI. In addition, DCNN with RMSProp Optimization was used for RFIC. In [13], a new two-step optical disk location and glaucoma diagnosis network was presented. In the primary step, a visual saliency mapping was integrated with a shallow CNN to locate effectual OD in the retinal image. TL-based pre-training approaches were used for glaucoma analysis during the secondary step. TL-based techniques, such as VGG-Net, Alex-Net, and Res-Net, were integrated with the saliency maps. In [14], a new multimodel DL network called G-EyeNet was presented to detect glaucoma in RFIs. G-EyeNet contained a deep convolutional Auto-Encoder (AE) and a classic CNN shared the encoded structure. The multi-model network had combined optimizations to minimize either image reconstruction or classifier error, depending on the multitask learning system.

In [15], a two-stage structure was investigated to identify and localize the optic disc and later classify it as glaucomatous or healthy. The primary phase depended on Regions with CNN (RCNN) and was responsible for localizing and extracting OD in RFI, but the secondary phase utilized DCNN to classify the extracted disc. So, a ruling-related semiautomated ground truth generating system was established, which offered essential annotations to train RCNN-based methods to automated disc localization. In [16], a new LSTM-based model was presented to exploit the sequence dependency of 1-D feature signal extraction in MAs and support its classifier from color fundus images. This method was trained to use 1-D intensity-based signals created in several patches of preprocessed fundus images.

III. THE PROPOSED METHOD

This study developed the innovative IWOADL-RFIGR method to retrieve and classify retinal fundus images. The proposed process consisted of different sub-processes, namely BF-based preprocessing, feature extraction, similarity measurement, classifying LS-SVM, and the IWOA tuning process. Figure 1 describes the comprehensive procedure of the IWOADL-RFIGR method.

Fig. 1. Comprehensive procedure of the IWOADL-RFIGR method.

A. Image Preprocessing

In the first phase, the proposed IWOADL-RFIGR method used the BF approach to preprocess the retinal images. The BF method is an edge-preserving, non-serial, and noise-reducing smooth filtering method, including two properties [17]. The process guarantees the conservation of sharp edges along with noise reduction. A BF of an image $f(x)$ can be determined as follows:

$$h(z) = k_r^{-1}(z) \int_{\Omega} f(\xi) c(\xi, z) s(f(\xi), f(z)) d\xi \quad (1)$$

with the normalizing:

$$k(z) = \int_{\Omega} c(\xi, z) s(f(\xi), f(z)) d\xi \quad (2)$$

where $c(\xi, z)$ measures the geometric proximity between the local regions centered on every point ξ and its adjacent pixel z , and $s(f(\xi), f(z))$ is an unbiased function that measures the photometric similarities between the central pixel z and its neighboring pixel ξ . The scientific representations of s and c in the above equations are determined as:

$$c(\xi, z) = \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\|\xi - z\|}{\sigma_d}\right)^2\right) \quad (3)$$

$$s(\xi, z) = \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\|f(\xi) - f(z)\|}{\sigma_r}\right)^2\right) \quad (4)$$

B. Image Retrieval Process

For image retrieval, the IWOADL-RFIGR method uses the lightweight CNN based on scratch learning with Euclidean distance-based similarity measurement. A well-generalized lightweight CNN with Scratch Learning (SL) was presented in [18]. This method integrates standard and depthwise separable convolution with skip connections and embeds the block of edge detection to improve the recognition ability. There are two typical convolution layers in the initial block of the method, having sizes of 3x3 and 1x1. It uses a bias regularizer of 0.01, a six-dilation rate, and a regularizer of 0.01. A nonlinear activation function and batch normalization (ReLU) was applied in the initial block to restrain the number of parameters and, simultaneously, to reinforce the network to offer a short description of the input images. Besides the typical convolutional block, there are six successive depthwise separable blocks that have both the dilation rate and depth multiplier parameters set at 6. In addition to the six blocks of the depthwise convolution layer, the sequence continues with the edge attention block. The real-time application of dropout was set at 0.25 to prevent overfitting after blocks 4, 5, and 6. The conventional model of max-pooling or average layers was not used due to the characteristics of spatial-dimensionality reduction. However, 1x1 convolution was applied in each block to reduce channel dimension. ReLU was used after every block. The padding within the typical and depthwise convolution blocks was employed as "the same". At the same time, the depth-multiplier rate was noted as six in the initial block of a typical convolutional layer. The last stage of the architecture consists of *k*-way sigmoid activation to generate distribution through *k*-class labeling in edge attention blocks to decide the concluding forecasting. After feature extraction, image retrieval takes place via Euclidean distance. The Euclidean distance between two points in Euclidean space is the length of the line segment between them. This was computed from the Cartesian coordinates of the points using the Pythagorean theorem.

C. Image Classification Process

The IWOADL-RFIGR method uses IWOA with the LS-SVM model for image classification. LS-SVM is an ML technique established in typical SVM [19]. SVMs are primarily used for classifier problems and non-linear function evaluation. Many researchers stated that SVM depends on regression systems, such as Support Vector Regression (SVR), for resolving particular modeling like predictive drives. Usually, the SVR network is established as:

$$f(x) = \langle \omega, \varphi(x) \rangle + b \quad (5)$$

where χ denotes the inputted database, $\langle \cdot \rangle$ represents the dot product, and ω , b , and $\varphi(x)$ imply the weight vectors, bias, and non-linear functions that map input spacing to higher dimension factor spacing. To make N count of data instances from the SVM, the optimized problem was determined as:

$$\min \frac{1}{2} \|\omega\|^2 + C \sum_{k=1}^N (\xi_k + \xi_k^*) S.T. \begin{cases} y_k - \langle \omega, \varphi(x_k) \rangle - b \leq \varepsilon + \xi, e \\ \langle \omega, \varphi(x_k) \rangle + b - y_k \leq \varepsilon + \xi_e^* \\ \xi, \xi_e^* \geq 0 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where ξ and ε denote the insensitive loss functioning and the slack variable, respectively. SVMs can model problems with higher-dimension input spaces and have been effectively used to model many hydrological procedures. At this point, the original term SVM can be used for either the predictive or classifier methods. However, due to the SVM's vital constrained optimized programming, it can undergo higher computation costs in modeling complicated phenomena. To resolve this problem, the LS-SVM method was used. In this study, the sum squared error and equality constraint of the cost function was applied for the training method as:

$$\min \frac{1}{2} \|\omega\|^2 + \frac{1}{2} \gamma \sum_{e=1}^N e_k^2 S.T. \begin{cases} \langle \omega, \varphi(x_k) \rangle + b + e_k \\ \gamma \geq 0 \\ k = 1, \dots, N \leq \varepsilon + \xi_{le} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where e_k refers to the error variable, and γ denotes a normalization constant. LS-SVM shortens the model process of SVM so that the resolution is delineated via the Karush-Kuhn-Tucker linear method. The presented linear method is merely resolved using an iterative method, including gradient-based optimization methodology. The predicted value (output) of the LS-SVM is evaluated by the following equation:

$$y(k) = \sum_{k=1}^N \alpha_k K(x, x_k) + b \quad (8)$$

where $K()$ signifies the kernel function considered an RBF for the kernel function as:

$$K(x, x_k) = \exp\left(-\frac{(x-x_k)^T(x-x_k)}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (9)$$

where σ defines the width of the kernel function.

The use of IWOA optimally chooses the parameters related to the LS-SVM model. It has a certain capability to escape from the local optima, a faster operational speed, and a simple adjustment parameter [20]. However, the algorithm exploits an arbitrary method for exploration, and overreliance on the random limit search speed of the model, convergence accuracy, and the speed of WOA increased. Furthermore, because of the constraint of the B coefficient vector, WOA loses its capability to escape from local optima once the iteration number reaches half of the maximal iteration. Consequently, WOA has a distinct possibility of falling into local optima, which leads to improper predictive outcomes. To resolve the abovementioned problems, this study presents an improved WOA, using Levy flight that has the best capability for escaping from the local optima, a fast convergence speed, and high convergence precision. Levy flight searching is based on Levy dispersion, which is a random-wise manner of larger range jump and smaller range search, and it can be represented as follows:

$$X(t+1) = X^*(t) - BD_1 \quad (10)$$

where t represents the current iteration amount, B and M represent the coefficient vectors:

$$B = 2aLevy(\lambda) - a \quad (11)$$

$$M = 2r_2 \tag{12}$$

where 1 is the constant upgrade distance size, H is the vector of coefficient, $X^*(t)$ is the location vector of the present optimum resolution, $X(t)$ is the existing location vector of humpback whales, $Xrand(t)$ is the random location vector, τ_p is the distance between the prey and the whale populace, a represents the parameter that is reduced from two to zero, ε defines the spiral movement shaping, m is a random vector within $[1, 1]$, and n is the probability parameter.

LWOA was used to resolve the optimization problems for TSVR. The LWOA is iteratively repeated to search for the concluding solution. In this study, the industrial trial dataset was normalized and used rapidly. Subsequently, the input variable was defined and nine input parameters were improved using the LWOA optimization. The population number was 30, the iteration number was 500, and the search range of the variable was $[1, 1]$. The initial iteration randomly generated 30 groups of the first solution, computed every set of resolutions fitness, and saved the set of resolutions with smaller fitness as a present optimum resolution for completing these iterations. Upon entering the following iteration, the position of 30 solutions was upgraded, and the set of solutions with lower fitness was related to the present optimum resolution to store the set of resolutions with the lowest fitness.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The performance evaluation of the IWOADL-RFIGR method was investigated using the DR Kaggle database [21] with 35126 samples and 5 class labels. Figure 2 shows some sample images and Figure 3 shows the sample retrieving outputs of the IWOADL-RFIGR method. The proposed method was simulated using Python 3.6.5 on an i5-8600K, GeForce 1050Ti 4GB, 250GB SSD, 16GB RAM, and 1TB HDD PC. The parameter settings were given as follows: learning rate: 0.01, dropout: 0.5, batch size: 5, epoch count: 50, and activation: ReLU. Figure 4 shows the confusion matrix of the IWOADL-RFIGR method. The results indicate that the IWOADL-RFIGR approach has a proficient classification of retinal fundus images.

Table I exhibits the comprehensive DR classifying outputs of the IWOADL-RFIGR method on 70:30 TR:TS of the dataset. The proposed method, with 70% TR, achieved average $accu_y$, $prec_n$, $reca_l$, F_{score} , and AUC_{score} of 99.69%, 97.53%, 98.40%, 97.96%, and 99.06%, respectively. Simultaneously, with 30% TS of the dataset, the IWOADL-RFIGR method achieved average $accu_y$, $prec_n$, $reca_l$, F_{score} , and AUC_{score} of 99.72%, 97.53%, 98.58%, 98.04%, and 99.16%, respectively. Table II demonstrates the respective DR classifying outputs of the proposed method on 80:20 TR:TS. On the 80% of the TR dataset, the proposed method achieved average $accu_y$, $prec_n$, $reca_l$, F_{score} , and AUC_{score} of 99.23%, 93.20%, 93.85%, 93.50%, and 96.58%, respectively. On the 20% of the TS dataset, the proposed method achieved average $accu_y$, $prec_n$, $reca_l$, F_{score} , and AUC_{score} of 99.33%, 93.10%, 95.52%, 94.25%, and 97.50%, respectively.

Fig. 2. Sample images.

Fig. 3. (a) Query Images, (b) retrieved Images.

TABLE I. RESULTS EVALUATION OF IWOADL-RFIGR UNDER 70:30 TR:TS DATA

Labels	$accu_y$	$prec_n$	$reca_l$	F_{score}	AUC_{score}
Training Stage (70%)					
1 st Class	99.36	99.70	99.43	99.56	99.29
2 nd Class	99.70	97.72	98.00	97.86	98.92
3 rd Class	99.70	98.68	99.32	99.00	99.54
4 th Class	99.84	96.83	96.67	96.75	98.30
5 th Class	99.86	94.74	98.58	96.62	99.23
Average	99.69	97.53	98.40	97.96	99.06
Testing Stage (30%)					
1 st Class	99.44	99.75	99.48	99.62	99.40
2 nd Class	99.75	98.25	98.25	98.25	99.06
3 rd Class	99.70	98.70	99.31	99.00	99.54
4 th Class	99.82	96.68	96.32	96.50	98.12
5 th Class	99.87	94.27	99.53	96.83	99.70
Average	99.72	97.53	98.58	98.04	99.16

Fig. 4. Confusion matrix of IWOADL-RFIGR: (a)-(b): 70:30 TR and TS dataset, and (c)-(d): 80:20 TR and TS dataset.

TABLE II. RESULTS EVALUATION OF IWOADL-RFIGR UNDER 80:20 TR:TS DATA

Labels	$accu_y$	$prec_n$	$reca_l$	F_{score}	AUC_{score}
Training Stage (80%)					
1 st Class	98.74	99.30	98.99	99.15	98.52
2 nd Class	99.33	95.15	95.00	95.07	97.32
3 rd Class	99.14	96.71	97.60	97.15	98.51
4 th Class	99.47	87.01	92.59	89.72	96.12
5 th Class	99.45	87.81	85.07	86.42	92.41
Average	99.23	93.20	93.85	93.50	96.58
Testing Stage (20%)					
1 st Class	99.00	99.57	99.06	99.32	98.95
2 nd Class	99.44	96.72	95.80	96.26	97.77
3 rd Class	99.20	97.13	97.68	97.41	98.58
4 th Class	99.42	83.85	94.15	88.71	96.85
5 th Class	99.60	88.24	90.91	89.55	95.34
Average	99.33	93.10	95.52	94.25	97.50

TABLE III. ACCURACY EVALUATION OF IWOADL-RFIGR WITH CURRENT ALGORITHMS [22]

Method	$accu_y$
IWOADL-RFIGR	99.72
RFIRC-ODL	99.61
WFDLN	98.00
Alex-Net	89.50
Mobile-Net	92.90
Xception	92.80
ResNet-50	94.51

Table III shows an overall comparison of the proposed IWOADL-RFIGR with other methods, in terms of $accu_y$. The proposed method achieved an $accu_y$ of 99.72%, while RFIRC-ODL, WFDLN, Alex-Net, Mobile-Net, Xception, and ResNet-50 approaches achieved 99.61%, 98%, 89.50%, 92.90%,

92.80%, and 94.51%, respectively. These results indicate the advanced efficiency of the proposed IWOADL-RFIGR method.

V. CONCLUSION

This study developed the innovative IWOADL-RFIGR method for retrieving and classifying retinal fundus images. In the first stage, the presented IWOADL-RFIGR method used the BF approach to preprocess the retinal images. For image retrieval, the IWOADL-RFIGR method used lightweight CNN based on scratch learning with Euclidean distance-based similarity measurement. Furthermore, the IWOADL-RFIGR method used IWOA with the LS-SVM method for image classification. The experimental validation of the proposed IWOADL-RFIGR method on the benchmark dataset exhibited better performance than other techniques. In the future, the proposed IWOADL-RFIGR method will be extended to the design of the deep instance segmentation process.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Imran, J. Li, Y. Pei, F. Akhtar, J.-J. Yang, and Y. Dang, "Automated identification of cataract severity using retinal fundus images," *Computer Methods in Biomechanics and Biomedical Engineering: Imaging & Visualization*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 691–698, Nov. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1080/21681163.2020.1806733>.
- [2] A. Shoukat, S. Akbar, S. A. E. Hassan, A. Rehman, and N. Ayesha, "An Automated Deep Learning Approach to Diagnose Glaucoma using Retinal Fundus Images," in *2021 International Conference on Frontiers of Information Technology (FIT)*, Islamabad, Pakistan, Sep. 2021, pp. 120–125, <https://doi.org/10.1109/FIT53504.2021.00031>.
- [3] M. Mateen, J. Wen, Nasrullah, S. Song, and Z. Huang, "Fundus Image Classification Using VGG-19 Architecture with PCA and SVD," *Symmetry*, vol. 11, no. 1, Jan. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.3390/sym11010001>.
- [4] M. Juneja, N. Thakur, S. Thakur, A. Uniyal, A. Wani, and P. Jindal, "GC-NET for classification of glaucoma in the retinal fundus image," *Machine Vision and Applications*, vol. 31, no. 5, Jun. 2020, Art. no. 38, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00138-020-01091-4>.
- [5] S. Goel *et al.*, "Deep Learning Approach for Stages of Severity Classification in Diabetic Retinopathy Using Color Fundus Retinal Images," *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, vol. 2021, Nov. 2021, Art. no. 7627566, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/7627566>.
- [6] D. R. Parashar and D. K. Agarwal, "SVM based Supervised Machine Learning Framework for Glaucoma Classification using Retinal Fundus Images," in *2021 10th IEEE International Conference on Communication Systems and Network Technologies (CSNT)*, Bhopal, India, Jun. 2021, pp. 660–663, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CSNT51715.2021.9509708>.
- [7] J. K. P. S. Yadav and S. Yadav, "Computer-aided diagnosis of cataract severity using retinal fundus images and deep learning," *Computational Intelligence*, vol. 38, no. 4, pp. 1450–1473, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1111/coin.12518>.
- [8] K. Shankar, A. R. W. Sait, D. Gupta, S. K. Lakshmanprabu, A. Khanna, and H. M. Pandey, "Automated detection and classification of fundus diabetic retinopathy images using synergic deep learning model," *Pattern Recognition Letters*, vol. 133, pp. 210–216, May 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patrec.2020.02.026>.
- [9] R. Poplin *et al.*, "Prediction of cardiovascular risk factors from retinal fundus photographs via deep learning," *Nature Biomedical Engineering*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 158–164, Mar. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41551-018-0195-0>.
- [10] S. Gupta, A. Panwar, S. Goel, A. Mittal, R. Nijhawan, and A. K. Singh, "Classification of Lesions in Retinal Fundus Images for Diabetic Retinopathy Using Transfer Learning," in *2019 International Conference on Information Technology (ICIT)*, Bhubaneswar, India, Sep. 2019, pp. 342–347, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIT48102.2019.00067>.

- [11] D. D. Van, "Application of Advanced Deep Convolutional Neural Networks for the Recognition of Road Surface Anomalies," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 10765–10768, Jun. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5890>.
- [12] A. Munshi, "Randomly-based Stepwise Multi-Level Distributed Medical Image Steganography," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 10922–10930, Jun. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5935>.
- [13] M. M. H. Milu, M. A. Rahman, M. A. Rashid, A. Kuwana, and H. Kobayashi, "Improvement of Classification Accuracy of Four-Class Voluntary-Imagery fNIRS Signals using Convolutional Neural Networks," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 10425–10431, Apr. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5703>.
- [14] A. Pal, M. R. Moorthy, and A. Shahina, "G-Eyenet: A Convolutional Autoencoding Classifier Framework for the Detection of Glaucoma from Retinal Fundus Images," in *2018 25th IEEE International Conference on Image Processing (ICIP)*, Athens, Greece, Jul. 2018, pp. 2775–2779, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIP.2018.8451029>.
- [15] M. N. Bajwa *et al.*, "Two-stage framework for optic disc localization and glaucoma classification in retinal fundus images using deep learning," *BMC Medical Informatics and Decision Making*, vol. 19, no. 1, Jul. 2019, Art. no. 136, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12911-019-0842-8>.
- [16] R. Acharya and N. B. Puhan, "Long Short-Term Memory Model Based Microaneurysm Sequence Classification in Fundus Images," in *2022 IEEE International Conference on Signal Processing and Communications (SPCOM)*, Bangalore, India, Jul. 2022, pp. 1–5, <https://doi.org/10.1109/SPCOM55316.2022.9840789>.
- [17] H. Yu, F. He, and Y. Pan, "A scalable region-based level set method using adaptive bilateral filter for noisy image segmentation," *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, vol. 79, no. 9, pp. 5743–5765, Mar. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-019-08493-1>.
- [18] N. Gour and P. Khanna, "Ocular diseases classification using a lightweight CNN and class weight balancing on OCT images," *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, vol. 81, no. 29, pp. 41765–41780, Dec. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-022-13617-1>.
- [19] R. M. A. Ikram, H.-L. Dai, A. A. Ewees, J. Shiri, O. Kisi, and M. Zounemat-Kermani, "Application of improved version of multi verse optimizer algorithm for modeling solar radiation," *Energy Reports*, vol. 8, pp. 12063–12080, Nov. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2022.09.015>.
- [20] C. Shi *et al.*, "Bending Force of Hot Rolled Strip Based on Improved Whale Optimization Algorithm and Twinning Support Vector Machine," *Metals*, vol. 12, no. 10, Oct. 2022, Art. no. 1589, <https://doi.org/10.3390/met12101589>.
- [21] "Diabetic Retinopathy Detection." <https://kaggle.com/competitions/diabetic-retinopathy-detection>.
- [22] G. U. Nneji, J. Cai, J. Deng, H. N. Monday, M. A. Hossin, and S. Nahar, "Identification of Diabetic Retinopathy Using Weighted Fusion Deep Learning Based on Dual-Channel Fundus Scans," *Diagnostics*, vol. 12, no. 2, Feb. 2022, Art. no. 540, <https://doi.org/10.3390/diagnostics12020540>.

Performance Analysis of Deep Transfer Learning Models for the Automated Detection of Cotton Plant Diseases

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ABSTRACT

Cotton is one of the most important agricultural products and is closely linked to the economic development of Pakistan. However, the cotton plant is susceptible to bacterial and viral diseases that can quickly spread and damage plants and ultimately affect the cotton yield. The automated and early detection of affected plants can significantly reduce the potential spread of the disease. This paper presents the implementation and performance analysis of bacterial blight and curl virus disease detection in cotton crops through deep learning techniques. The automated disease detection is performed through transfer learning of six pre-trained deep learning models, namely DenseNet121, DenseNet169, MobileNetV2, ResNet50V2, VGG16, and VGG19. A total of 1362 images of local agricultural fields and 1292 images from online resources were used to train and validate the models. Image augmentation techniques were performed to increase the dataset diversity and size. Transfer learning was implemented for different image resolutions ranging from 32×32 to 256×256 pixels. Performance metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1 Score, and prediction time were evaluated for each implemented model. The results indicate higher accuracy, up to 96%, for DenseNet169 and ResNet50V2 models when trained on the 256×256 pixels image dataset. The lowest accuracy, 52%, was obtained by the MobileNetV2 model when trained on low-resolution, 32×32, images. The confusion matrix analysis indicates the true-positive prediction rates higher than 91% for fresh leaves, 87% for bacterial blight, and 76% for curl virus detection for all implemented models when trained and tested on an image dataset of 128×128 pixels or higher resolution.

Keywords-transfer learning; CNN; pretrained networks; disease detection; classification; cotton plants

I. INTRODUCTION

The agriculture sector plays a significant role in generating revenue and catering to the food demand [1]. It is the backbone

of any country and works as a primary source of income for a large proportion of the people, particularly in developing countries. Cotton is a cash crop and produces natural fiber which is essential for the textile manufacturing industry. It is

also an important source of vegetable oil and cottonseed cake. About 50% of the global population depends on cotton-related materials. The cotton plant's protection from diseases is very crucial as it significantly impacts the productivity of cotton yield. Detection of cotton plant diseases is a challenging task. It is difficult to distinguish between different diseases of cotton plants due to the harsh outdoor environment and complex structure of plant leaves with similarity in appearances. The cotton plant is susceptible to various diseases such as bacterial light, root knot nematode, fusarium wilt, root rot, and verticillium wilt. Traditional methods of disease detection such as visual inspection and laboratory analysis are time-consuming, labor-intensive, and often inaccurate. It is crucial to diagnose cotton diseases at an early stage to prevent the spread of diseases. Thus, efficient and effective methods for cotton crop disease detection are required. Computer vision-based system machine learning systems are developed for the accurate detection of diseases in cotton crops.

Deep learning-based Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) models are extensively employed in the agriculture field to recognize different plant diseases and pests, classify fruits, and identify weeds [3-7]. They are powerful tools for solving complex problems in various fields. Deep learning is an automatic learning method based on a multilayer network. The effectiveness of such learning techniques in the agricultural field has been proved [8].

In the current work, deep learning-based models are implemented for the automated detection of cotton crop diseases with high accuracy. Six different pre-trained CNN models were trained using the transfer learning approach: DenseNet121, DenseNet169, MobileNetV2, ResNet50V2, VGG16, and VGG19. The plant image dataset indicating bacterial blight, curl virus, and healthy leaves were collected from local cotton crop fields to train and validate the transfer learning-based CNN model. The performance metrics of all trained models are evaluated and compared. The current work can be used in the field to recognize the different diseases at an early stage and thus to increase cotton productivity.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

There are numerous studies that classify and identify cotton crop leaf diseases [9]. Authors in [10] collected cotton leaf images from the field and prepared a dataset of healthy and unhealthy leaves. They employed four different ML techniques, i.e. CNN, VGG16, novel meta deep learning, and ResNet50 on the augmented data. They developed a generalized meta learning-based model to detect different diseases such as bacterial blight, leaf spot, powdery mildew, and leaf curl with an accuracy of 98.53%. Authors in [11] used ResNet50 and VGG16-based transfer learning models to detect crop diseases. Authors in [12] developed a CNN-based model to detect cotton diseases and pests, such as leaf miner, spider mite, and bacterial blight. The K-fold cross-validation approach was used to split and augment the dataset. The model had an overall accuracy of 96.4%. Authors in [13] used a Deep Convolutional Neural Network (D-CNN)-based DCPLD-CNN model to classify and detect cotton plant and leaf diseases. They found that existing techniques have some limitations to detect Malvacearum and leaf roll dwarf viruses. They used pre-

trained architectures and added extra dense layers to fine-tune the developed DCNN model, obtaining an identification accuracy of 98.60%. Authors in [14] used a deep-learning approach to identify cotton plant diseases. They integrated a CNN-based model with the softmax layer and a pre-trained ResNet model for image classification. The focal loss function was used to improve the model's ability to learn smaller features. They recommended implementing the model on mobile devices to facilitate the farmers so that they can detect cotton crop diseases in real-time. Authors in [15] studied smart farming techniques and the parameters essential for increasing productivity in modern agriculture. They used a decision tree classifier based on the data of different parameters such as temperature and soil moisture to predict the diseases of cotton crops. Authors in [16] proposed a robust hybrid Automated Cotton crop Disease Recognition (ACDR) system. The results showed that the model has auratic and visual features and it has outperformed the existing models. The model has 89.08% sensitivity and 41% specificity which is higher than the SIFT (Scale-Invariant Feature Transform) and SASI-based ACDRs.

Authors in [17] presented an automated image processing-based system for the diagnosis of cotton leaf diseases. They used a dataset of 130 images to train an SVM classifier. The dataset consists of 50 bacterial blight images, 50 magnesium deficiency images, and 30 images of healthy plants. The classification of the images was based on features such as color and texture of images, achieving an accuracy of 98.46%. Authors in [18-19] employed pre-trained GoogleNet in their models to classify diseases of various crops, achieving accuracy of 94% and 99.53%. Authors in [20] used a quadruped robot to capture images of the cotton field. They developed a ConvNeXt-based cotton crop detection system with a Multiscale Spatial Pyramid Attention (MSPA) module. The ConvNeXt with MSPA achieved accuracy in the range of 97.2% to 100% on different datasets of cotton. Authors in [21] developed a web-based system for cotton crop disease detection using CNNs. They trained the model with 141 images of each disease and achieved an accuracy of 80%. Authors in [22] employed numerous deep-learning approaches to recognize different plant leaf diseases. They developed a camera-based real-time automated system for collecting images of cotton crops. The VGG16 network showed the best performance among different Machine Learning (ML) models and achieved 99.908% accuracy. Authors in [23, 24] developed a hardware-based prototype for plant disease recognition and classification. They used Raspberry Pi 4 and Arduino microcontrollers in the hardware prototypes. Authors in [25, 26] developed a robotic system for the detection of plant diseases. They used different ML algorithms such as the principal component analysis algorithm, Densenet121, ResNet34, ResNet50, and VGG-16. The system achieved an accuracy of 98.3%. Authors in [27] built an efficient and automated robot to remove diseases-infected plants from the stem. The robot identifies the leaf diseases in cotton plants and removes them. In summary, deep learning-based techniques may deliver many opportunities in the agriculture sector by monitoring the health of plants in real-time using deep learning helps to identify the diseases at early stages.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Pre-trained CNN Models

CNNs can automatically learn and extract meaningful features from huge data sets by reducing the need for manual feature extraction. They facilitate prior learning by training the model on the large-scale generalized dataset. Pre-trained models can be trained for the new task by using the available dataset which modifies the final layers of the pre-trained network. In this study, six pre-trained models are used. They are trained on new data sets for the detection of bacterial blight, curl virus, and fresh leaves in cotton plants. The main features and properties of the pre-trained models are discussed below.

1) DenseNet121

It is a CNN architecture with 121 weight layers and dense connections among layers [28]. The model has 8 million parameters and efficiently captures complex input-output relationships. It is pre-trained on ImageNet and suitable for different computer vision tasks such as object detection, semantic segmentation, and image classification.

2) DenseNet169

It comprises 169 weight layers and dense connections between each layer [29]. The model consists of approximately 14 million parameters and efficiently captures complex relationships. It is trained with ImageNet similar to the DenseNet121 model with 1 million images and 100 classes. The shallow architecture and dense connections in the model provide improved and computationally efficient performance on complex data.

3) MobileNetV2

MobileNetV2 is a compact CNN architecture offered by Google AI for devices having limited computational resources [30]. It provides high accuracy and efficient computational power and minimum power consumption. The model has 3.5 million parameters, which makes it lightweight and easy to deploy on mobile and embedded devices. The use of depth-wise separable convolutions and inverted residual blocks in the model captures complex relationships. It is suitable for deployment on devices with limited computational resources.

4) ResNet50V2

ResNet50V2 is a variation of the ResNet50 deep CNN architecture with improved learning ability [31]. It uses identity shortcuts and batch normalization to capture complex input data representations. The model has 50 weight layers and is trained on the ImageNet dataset. Compared to other popular models, the ResNet50V2 has a deeper architecture but is shallower than ResNet50.

5) VGG16

It is a well-known CNN architecture introduced in 2014 [32]. The architecture is characterized by its uniform design, where all layers have the same number of filters and filter size, which reduces overfitting and enhances the model's ability to generalize to new data. The VGG16 architecture consists of 16 weight layers and comprises 13 convolutional layers, 5 max-pooling layers, and 3 fully connected layers.

6) VGG19

It is primarily designed for image classification tasks [33]. In contrast to VGG16, it comprises 19 layers including 6 convolutional layers and 3 fully connected layers resulting in a significant number of parameters (approximately 143 million as compared to the 138 million for VGG16). VGG19 remains a popular choice for transfer learning due to its strong performance across a wide range of image classification tasks and its ability to extract useful features from images. The large number of parameters in VGG19 allows for the learning of complex image representations, making it an ideal starting point for fine-tuning new image classification tasks.

B. Data Collection and Augmentation

The dataset used in this study consists of images collected from the local agriculture fields and online sources. The cotton crop images were collected from two distinct locations in Pakistan, namely Tando Allahyar and Kotri. The local dataset collection allowed the training of model on real-world data which increases the models' reliability for local implementation. The dataset includes 562 images of fresh cotton leaves, 300 images of cotton leaves with curl virus, and 500 images of bacterial blight. Figure 1(a) shows the class-wise distribution of images acquired from both locations. Moreover, 1,292 images representing the same classes were sourced from Kaggle [34]. Thus, a combined dataset of 2,654 unique images was utilized for training and testing of the models.

Fig. 1. (a) The quantified distribution images collected from local sites and sourced from Kaggle, (b) sample images collected from Tando Allahyar, Pakistan, (c) sample images collected from Kotri, Pakistan, and (d) the sample images collected from Kaggle.

To optimize the training of a deep CNN model, a large quantity of training images is necessary. We employed the image data augmentation technique to increase the number of images and to introduce dataset variations. The data augmentation increased the diversity of the input, expanded its generalization capacity, and reduced the risk of overfitting. The data augmentation process included flipping, rotation, shifting, scaling, shearing, and scaling of all available images proving a total of 13,270 images which were then utilized for the model training and validation. Figure 2 shows the distribution of training and validation dataset images for each class after the augmentation.

C. Model Implementation and Transfer Learning

The training and validation implementation of pre-trained models involved 5 main steps as represented in the block diagram in Figure 3. The first step included the acquisition and organization of the dataset in a local repository. In the second step, the image augmentation techniques were applied as discussed in the previous section. The dataset annotation for three classes, bacterial blight, curl virus, and fresh leaves, was performed in the third step which also includes the splitting of images into training and validation image sets. 70% of the total images were used for training the models while the remaining 30% were used during validation. In the next step, the training validation sets were fed to the pre-trained CNN model for transfer learning, where the weights of the models were fine-tuned based on the supplied dataset. Transfer learning leverages the knowledge acquired from a prior task to improve generalization performance for the new task. The pre-trained network is modified by replacing the final few layers with new layers, including a fully connected layer and a softmax classification layer, where the number of classes is three in the current study representing fresh leaves, curl virus, and bacterial blight.

Fig. 2. Distribution of the augmented image dataset representing each class and segmented to training and validation sets.

Fig. 3. Implementation block diagram for the transfer learning of pre-trained models with augmented and annotated datasets.

Each model underwent layer unfreezing, accompanied by the addition of an activation layer, a batch-normalization layer, and a dropout layer. The models were tested using consistent values for dropout, learning rate, and batch size, with varying input image sizes of 32×32 , 64×64 , 128×128 , and 256×256 pixels. The training was performed with a learning rate of

0.0001, a batch size of 32, and 200 epochs, which were chosen after the established best practices in the field. Once the transfer learning process was complete, the weights of the trained models were evaluated for each image size in terms of accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, and confusion matrix. The confusion matrix is a graphical representation that summarizes the performance of the model by showing the number of correct and incorrect predictions for each class. It consists of four metrics: True Positive (TP), False Positive (FP), False Negative (FN), and True Negative (TN). TP represents the number of correctly predicted positive instances, while FP represents the number of negative instances incorrectly predicted as positive. FN represents the number of positive instances incorrectly predicted as negative, while TN represents the number of correctly predicted negative instances. The models were trained using Google Colab on a Tesla T4 GPU running 525.85.12 driver version and 12.0 CUDA version. Subsequently, the trained models were tested on a laptop computer equipped with 8 GB of RAM, a 2.40GHz Intel Core-i5 CPU, and an Intel HD Graphics 520. All implementations were performed on Jupyter Notebook IDE on a Windows 10 operating system.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The confusion matrix of each implemented model was analyzed for the different resolutions of the image dataset and a thorough comparison was performed between the different models. The primary objective of this analysis was to provide insight into the performance of each model and facilitate the selection of the most effective one for the proposed task. The performance of the implemented models for the detection of cotton plant diseases was evaluated by employing commonly used performance metrics used for the classification task. The classification report provides a succinct summary of essential classification metrics such as training accuracy, validation accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. These metrics are derived by comparing the model's predictions to the true values present in the data. Training accuracy is a measure of the model performance on the training set, while validation accuracy indicates the model performance on the validation set. Precision quantifies the proportion of TPs among all the samples that were predicted as positive, whereas recall measures the proportion of TPs among all the genuinely positive samples. The F1 score represents the harmonic mean of precision and recall, providing a single performance metric that can be used to compare the overall effectiveness of the model.

Figure 4 shows the training accuracy vs the number of epochs for all the implemented models. The result indicates lower model accuracy, as observed in Figure 4(a) when the training is performed at an image dataset resolution of 32×32 pixels. Similarly, it is also noticed that the accuracy does not improve after the 50 epochs and mainly remains within the limited range of 45-75% for all the implemented models. It is also noticed that the training accuracy of MobileNetV2 is lower while the best accuracy is observed for DenseNet169. Moreover, the analysis of Figure 4 indicates a significant improvement in training accuracy as the pixel resolution of the image dataset is increased. The DenseNet169 and ResNet50V2

show the highest accuracy, up to 96%, when trained on 256x256 pixel images. The lowest accuracy, 52%, is observed for MobileNetV2 implementation when trained on 32x32 pixels images. DenseNet169 achieved 96% efficiency due to its dense connections in its model architecture, which promote information flow and feature reuse, providing an advantage for cotton crop disease identification on the gathered dataset over other models. ResNet50V2's model design overcomes vanishing gradients and stabilizes training using identity shortcuts and batch normalization. The residual connections in its design provide smooth gradient flow, while batch normalization minimizes variance, resulting in increased performance when compared to competing models.

The confusion matrix was obtained to evaluate the prediction capability for each implemented model. Figure 5 shows the consolidated representation of the confusion matrix for all the implemented models at different resolutions of the image dataset. The results indicate a significant number of FPs and TNs for most of the classes when the 32x32 image dataset is chosen. The higher number of incorrect predictions is associated with the low resolution of training and validation images. Figure 5 further indicates improved TP predictions when the image size increased to 256x256 pixels, which can be observed by looking at the diagonal values at the bottom half of

the figure. The overall results indicate the average TP prediction rate greater than 89% for all models when they are trained and validated on high resolution (256x256) images.

Fig. 4. Training accuracy of the implemented models vs the number of the epochs for image sizes of (a) 32x32, (b) 64x64, (c) 128x128, and (d) 256x256 pixels.

TABLE I. DETAILED PERFORMANCE METRICS OF ALL IMPLEMENTED MODELS

	Classification	Performance metrics															
		Precision				Recall				F1-Score				Accuracy			
		32x32	64x64	128x128	256x256	32x32	64x64	128x128	256x256	32x32	64x64	128x128	256x256	32x32	64x64	128x128	256x256
DenseNet 121	Bacterial Blight	0.64	0.75	0.8	0.91	0.53	0.83	0.84	0.92	0.58	0.79	0.82	0.92	0.73	0.84	0.92	0.95
	Curl Virus	0.64	0.79	0.79	0.89	0.48	0.73	0.82	0.83	0.55	0.76	0.81	0.86				
	Healthy Leave	0.63	0.79	0.88	0.88	0.86	0.76	0.82	0.92	0.73	0.77	0.85	0.9				
DenseNet 169	Bacterial Blight	0.68	0.74	0.83	0.95	0.6	0.79	0.89	0.88	0.64	0.76	0.86	0.92	0.74	0.85	0.93	0.96
	Curl Virus	0.48	0.74	0.95	0.88	0.39	0.66	0.65	0.89	0.43	0.7	0.77	0.89				
	Healthy Leave	0.77	0.95	0.83	0.91	0.98	0.97	0.98	0.96	0.86	0.96	0.9	0.93				
MobileNetV2	Bacterial Blight	0.52	0.7	0.86	0.9	0.46	0.77	0.92	0.93	0.49	0.73	0.89	0.91	0.52	0.81	0.95	0.95
	Curl Virus	0.46	0.69	0.89	0.97	0.44	0.6	0.78	0.77	0.45	0.64	0.83	0.86				
	Healthy Leave	0.59	0.87	0.89	0.87	0.68	0.89	0.92	0.98	0.63	0.88	0.91	0.92				
ResNet50V2	Bacterial Blight	0.57	0.94	0.88	0.95	0.58	0.67	0.9	0.96	0.57	0.79	0.89	0.95	0.6	0.84	0.93	0.96
	Curl Virus	0.59	0.87	0.91	0.94	0.41	0.77	0.87	0.9	0.49	0.81	0.89	0.92				
	Healthy Leave	0.63	0.7	0.91	0.94	0.77	0.96	0.92	0.95	0.69	0.81	0.91	0.95				
VGG16	Bacterial Blight	0.62	0.73	0.73	0.89	0.73	0.82	0.97	0.95	0.67	0.77	0.83	0.92	0.66	0.76	0.89	0.94
	Curl Virus	0.5	0.73	0.89	0.89	0.35	0.6	0.71	0.85	0.41	0.66	0.79	0.87				
	Healthy Leave	0.65	0.82	0.92	0.93	0.69	0.85	0.78	0.91	0.67	0.83	0.84	0.92				
VGG19	Bacterial Blight	0.68	0.71	0.68	0.87	0.76	0.86	0.88	0.87	0.72	0.78	0.77	0.87	0.65	0.75	0.85	0.93
	Curl Virus	0.57	0.71	0.78	0.95	0.56	0.43	0.79	0.82	0.57	0.54	0.78	0.88				
	Healthy Leave	0.72	0.74	0.83	0.85	0.69	0.83	0.59	0.94	0.69	0.78	0.69	0.9				

Fig. 5. Confusion matrices for lowest and highest image resolutions for all implemented models.

V. CONCLUSION

This work presented the implementation and performance analysis of automated disease detection in cotton plants based on the transfer learning of six state-of-the-art pre-trained deep learning networks that included DenseNet121, DenseNet169, MobileNetV2, ResNet50V2, VGG16, and VGG19. The two most common diseases of cotton plants, i.e. bacterial blight, and curl virus were considered. A significant part of the image dataset covering the target diseases was collected from local fields in Pakistan. Standard image augmentation techniques were applied to increase the size and versatility of the dataset. The transfer learning was implemented for four different image resolutions representing the multiple levels of image features. The performance comparison of the implemented models indicated lower accuracy when trained on low-resolution images. The inter-model comparison suggested the DenseNet169 model as most accurate providing training accuracy up to 96%.

The present work provides practical insight for implementing transfer learning models to real-time cotton disease detection systems. However, it still has some limitations which require further investigation. The current study includes a limited local dataset collected from two locations only. The reliability and accuracy of the models can be further improved by collecting datasets across the country with diverse geographical and climate features. Additionally, the current implementation is performed on CPU which limits its practical use. The future implementation of models on mobile platforms such as smartphones and embedded controllers will escalate its impact and enable its reach to end users.

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REFERENCES

- [1] X. E. Pantazi, D. Moshou, and A. A. Tamouridou, "Automated leaf disease detection in different crop species through image features analysis and One Class Classifiers," *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, vol. 156, pp. 96–104, Jan. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2018.11.005>.
- [2] M. Martineau, D. Conte, R. Raveaux, I. Arnault, D. Munier, and G. Venturini, "A survey on image-based insect classification," *Pattern Recognition*, vol. 65, pp. 273–284, May 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patcog.2016.12.020>.
- [3] Y. Toda and F. Okura, "How Convolutional Neural Networks Diagnose Plant Disease," *Plant Phenomics*, vol. 2019, Mar. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.34133/2019/9237136>.
- [4] Y. Lu, S. Yi, N. Zeng, Y. Liu, and Y. Zhang, "Identification of rice diseases using deep convolutional neural networks," *Neurocomputing*, vol. 267, pp. 378–384, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neucom.2017.06.023>.
- [5] L. Loyani and D. Machuve, "A Deep Learning-based Mobile Application for Segmenting Tuta Absoluta's Damage on Tomato Plants," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7730–7737, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4355>.
- [6] S. Alqethami, B. Almtanni, W. Alzhrani, and M. Alghamdi, "Disease Detection in Apple Leaves Using Image Processing Techniques," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 8335–8341, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4721>.
- [7] S. Nuanmeesri, "A Hybrid Deep Learning and Optimized Machine Learning Approach for Rose Leaf Disease Classification," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7678–7683, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4455>.
- [8] A. Gutierrez, A. Ansuategi, L. Susperregi, C. Tubfo, I. Rankić, and L. Lenža, "A Benchmarking of Learning Strategies for Pest Detection and Identification on Tomato Plants for Autonomous Scouting Robots Using Internal Databases," *Journal of Sensors*, vol. 2019, May 2019, Art. no. e5219471, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/5219471>.
- [9] S. Kumar *et al.*, "A Comparative Analysis of Machine Learning Algorithms for Detection of Organic and Nonorganic Cotton Diseases," *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, vol. 2021, p. e1790171, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/1790171>.
- [10] M. S. Memon, P. Kumar, and R. Iqbal, "Meta Deep Learn Leaf Disease Identification Model for Cotton Crop," *Computers*, vol. 11, no. 7, Jul. 2022, Art. no. 102, <https://doi.org/10.3390/computers11070102>.
- [11] A. K. Rangarajan, R. Purushothaman, and A. Ramesh, "Tomato crop disease classification using pre-trained deep learning algorithm," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 133, pp. 1040–1047, Jan. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2018.07.070>.
- [12] A. M., M. Zekiwo, and A. Bruck, "Deep Learning-Based Image Processing for Cotton Leaf Disease and Pest Diagnosis," *Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 2021, Jun. 2021, Art. no. e9981437, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/9981437>.
- [13] M. R. Ahmed, "Leveraging Convolutional Neural Network and Transfer Learning for Cotton Plant and Leaf Disease Recognition," *International Journal of Image, Graphics and Signal Processing*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 47–62, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.5815/ijgisp.2021.04.04>.
- [14] V. Rajasekar, K. Venu, S. R. Jena, R. J. Varthini, and S. Ishwarya, "Detection of Cotton Plant Diseases Using Deep Transfer Learning," *Journal of Mobile Multimedia*, pp. 307–324, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.13052/jmm1550-4646.1828>.
- [15] J. Chopda, H. Raveshiya, S. Nakum, and V. Nakrani, "Cotton Crop Disease Detection using Decision Tree Classifier," in *2018 International Conference on Smart City and Emerging Technology (ICSCET)*, Mumbai, India, Jan. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSCET.2018.8537336>.
- [16] K. Prashar, R. Talwar, and C. Kant, "Robust Automatic Cotton Crop Disease Recognition (ACDR) Method using the Hybrid Feature Descriptor with SVM," in *INDIACom-2017*, New Delhi, India, Mar. 2017.
- [17] N. R. Bhimte and V. R. Thool, "Diseases Detection of Cotton Leaf Spot Using Image Processing and SVM Classifier," in *2018 Second International Conference on Intelligent Computing and Control Systems (ICICCS)*, Madurai, India, Jun. 2018, pp. 340–344, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCONS.2018.8662906>.
- [18] J. G. Arnal Barbedo, "Plant disease identification from individual lesions and spots using deep learning," *Biosystems Engineering*, vol. 180, pp. 96–107, Apr. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2019.02.002>.
- [19] S. P. Mohanty, D. P. Hughes, and M. Salathé, "Using Deep Learning for Image-Based Plant Disease Detection," *Frontiers in Plant Science*, vol. 7, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2016.01419>.
- [20] Y. Tao, F. Chang, Y. Huang, L. Ma, L. Xie, and H. Su, "Cotton Disease Detection Based on ConvNeXt and Attention Mechanisms," *IEEE Journal of Radio Frequency Identification*, vol. 6, pp. 805–809, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1109/JRFID.2022.3206841>.
- [21] S. Kumbhar, A. Nilawar, S. Patil, B. Mahalakshmi, and M. Nipane, "Farmer Buddy-Web Based Cotton Leaf Disease Detection Using CNN," *International Journal of Applied Engineering Research*, vol. 14, no. 11, pp. 2662–2666, 2019.
- [22] S. A. Sabeeh and S. H. Ameen, "Detection and Classification of Leaf Disease Using Deep Learning for a Greenhouses' Robot," *Iraqi Journal*

- of Computer, Communication, Control and System Engineering, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 15–28, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.33103/uot.ijccce.21.4.2>.
- [23] E. A. H. Mora, V. González-Huitrón, A. E. Rodríguez-Mata, and H. R. Rangel, "Convolutional Neural Networks-based plant disease detection implemented on low-power consumption device," in *2021 IEEE International Autumn Meeting on Power, Electronics and Computing (ROPEC)*, Ixtapa, Mexico, Aug. 2021, vol. 5, pp. 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ROPEC53248.2021.9668160>.
- [24] M. H. Jumat, M. S. Nazmudeen, and A. T. Wan, "Smart farm prototype for plant disease detection, diagnosis & treatment using IoT device in a greenhouse," in *7th Brunei International Conference on Engineering and Technology 2018 (BICET 2018)*, Bandar Seri Begawan, Brunei, Aug. 2018, pp. 1–4, <https://doi.org/10.1049/cp.2018.1545>.
- [25] N. Schor, A. Bechar, T. Ignat, A. Dombrovsky, Y. Elad, and S. Berman, "Robotic Disease Detection in Greenhouses: Combined Detection of Powdery Mildew and Tomato Spotted Wilt Virus," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 354–360, Jan. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1109/LRA.2016.2518214>.
- [26] S. H. Abed, A. S. Al-Waisy, H. J. Mohammed, and S. Al-Fahdawi, "A modern deep learning framework in robot vision for automated bean leaves diseases detection," *International Journal of Intelligent Robotics and Applications*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 235–251, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41315-021-00174-3>.
- [27] M. S. P. Rahul and M. Rajesh, "Image processing based Automatic Plant Disease Detection and Stem Cutting Robot," in *2020 Third International Conference on Smart Systems and Inventive Technology (ICSSIT)*, Tirunelveli, India, Dec. 2020, pp. 889–894, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSSIT48917.2020.9214257>.
- [28] A. S. Vellaichamy, A. Swaminathan, C. Varun, and K. S., "Multiple Plant Leaf Disease Classification Using Densenet-121 Architecture," *International Journal of Electrical Engineering and Technology*, vol. 12, no. 5, May 2021, <https://doi.org/10.34218/IJEET.12.5.2021.005>.
- [29] V. Sathiesh Kumar and S. Anubha Pearline, "Real-Time Plant Species Recognition Using Non-averaged DenseNet-169 Deep Learning Paradigm," in *Computer Vision and Image Processing, 2023*, pp. 58–72, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-31417-9_5.
- [30] M. Sandler, A. Howard, M. Zhu, A. Zhmoginov, and L.-C. Chen, "MobileNetV2: Inverted Residuals and Linear Bottlenecks," presented at the 2018 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR), Jun. 2018, pp. 4510–4520, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2018.00474>.
- [31] M. Rahimzadeh and A. Attar, "A modified deep convolutional neural network for detecting COVID-19 and pneumonia from chest X-ray images based on the concatenation of Xception and ResNet50V2," *Informatics in Medicine Unlocked*, vol. 19, 2020, Art. no. 100360, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.imu.2020.100360>.
- [32] H. Qassim, A. Verma, and D. Feinzimer, "Compressed residual-VGG16 CNN model for big data places image recognition," in *2018 IEEE 8th Annual Computing and Communication Workshop and Conference (CCWC)*, Las Vegas, NV, USA, Jan. 2018, pp. 169–175, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CCWC.2018.8301729>.
- [33] L. Wen, X. Li, X. Li, and L. Gao, "A New Transfer Learning Based on VGG-19 Network for Fault Diagnosis," in *2019 IEEE 23rd International Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work in Design (CSCWD)*, Porto, Portugal, Feb. 2019, pp. 205–209, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CSCWD.2019.8791884>.
- [34] "Cotton Plant Disease Prediction CNN (96.8% acc)." <https://kaggle.com/code/aravindaraman/cotton-plant-disease-prediction-cnn-96-8-acc>.

A New Approach on the Egyptian Black Sand Ilmenite Alteration Processes

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ABSTRACT

Several studies have investigated the process of alteration of ilmenite, especially in black sand. To predict the mechanisms of ilmenite alteration and the role of some minor element oxides in the alteration process, separated non-magnetic altered ilmenite grains were examined using a binocular microscope and a Cameca SX-100 microprobe instrument. Twenty intergrown phases of alteration products were concluded in three postulated scenarios for the following alteration processes, carried out after forming the most stable lowest Leached pseudorutile (LPSR) phase $\text{FeTi}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_3$. Most of the alteration phases of pseudorutile (PSR) and LPSR have real $\text{Ti}/(\text{Ti}+\text{Fe})$ ratios between 0.6 and 0.75. Some misleading calculations of definite analyzed ilmenite alteration spots showed that all the analyzed TiO_2 percentage is contained within the chemical formula of the analyzed LPSR phase. In these cases, the false $\text{Ti}/(\text{Ti}+\text{Fe})$ ratios attain up to 0.9, the false included total number of anions (O, OH) ranges between 7 and 8.5, and the associated molecular water ranged between half and two water molecules (0.5-2 H_2O). In these cases, the structure of the remaining LPSR phase may be intergrown with a separated individual triple rutile phase, which appears to have the same X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) pattern as the single PSR phase, or intergrown with a cryptocrystalline TiO_2 phase. Some molecular formulas of PSR or Hydroxylated PSR (HPSR) from previous studies were discussed and explained following the proposed approach.

Keywords-Egypt; black sand; altered ilmenite; leached pseudorutile; hydroxylated pseudorutile

I. INTRODUCTION

Several studies have investigated the alteration products of ilmenite, and various definitions have been proposed for leucoxene. Identification of the intermediate altered compound pseudorutile (PSR) was difficult in earlier studies due to its appearance in fine grain size (30°A), its poor crystallinity, and the similarity of most of its diffraction lines with those of other phases [1]. Thus, it is safe to say that the distinct isotropic phase, previously called arizonite, amorphous iron titanate, and pro-arizonite, was PSR [2-4]. The name PSR was proposed for the product of oxidation and progressive partial removal of iron due to the alteration of ilmenite that produces an intermediate iron titanate of a definite structure [5]. Ilmenite can be altered under reducing conditions [6-7]. The change from ilmenite to PSR involves a phase change in the oxide structure [8]. According to [9], the alteration of ilmenite to PSR decreases cell volume by up to 13%, while it is 6% and reaches 40% by alteration to leucoxene, leading to shrinkage cracks [10]. There are more extensive nanopore networks in the Hydroxylated PSR (HPSR) than in PSR [11]. The detrital ilmenite grains of heavy mineral sands in Brazil are sometimes extremely altered in PSR, anatase (grain boundaries), and leucoxene [12]. There are two types of detrital ilmenite alteration. Type I is an alteration sequence of ilmenite-hydrated ilmenite-PSR-leucoxene, and in Type II, ilmenite is directly altered to HPSR [10]. Type II alteration involves dissolution-reprecipitation [10, 13] or dissolution-hydration [11].

PSR is an intermediate alteration product that commonly occurs in the early stages of alteration (weathering or early diagenesis under weakly reducing conditions) and alters to leucoxene during continued diagenesis [14]. Leucoxene is as conductive as rutile but more magnetic, as rutile is nonmagnetic [15]. Several types of magnetic and non-magnetic altered ilmenite varieties were detected in [16], which explained the formation of each of these altered varieties. The alteration process of Egyptian beach ilmenite was investigated in [17-20]. The chemical composition of highly altered leucoxenated Egyptian beach ilmenite grains was examined using a scanning electron microscope, showing that TiO_2 ranged between 59.45 and 89.72 wt%, the total iron content (Fe_2O_3) ranged from 2.34 to 32.68 wt%, and the SiO_2 content ranged from 0.89 to 8.19 wt% [21]. In some leucoxenated grains, residual particles of ilmenite were enclosed in many of the altered ilmenite grains and some grains were still preserved with the crystal form of the parent ilmenite [22].

Most of the mineralogical features and textures of an obtained high-grade ilmenite concentrate were investigated in [23-24]. According to [25-26], altered ilmenite grains have a wide range of magnetic mass susceptibilities. They can be separated as magnetic at a wide range of 0.1 and 1 A. The highly altered leucoxenated grains (secondary rutile) are separated as nonmagnetic at 1 A. The altered ilmenite grains, which are separated as magnetic at 0.5 and 1 A, contain an enrichment of altered silicate minerals, silica, sphene, and

individual phases of Ti and Fe as oxyhydroxides and TiO_2 . In addition, relatively higher contents of structural water are detected in the molecular formulas of the investigated LPSR phases, in addition to considerable volumes of voids and cracks. These are the reasons for the relatively lower magnetic characteristics of these grains. However, leucoxene may be defined as a partially or completely altered ilmenite having a wide range of chemical compositions, which embarrass the recorded crystal structure and may not represent all the included alteration phases. Some or all altered phases may be amorphous, crypto- or micro-crystalline, or have an identical X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) pattern. This study investigated the altered ilmenite grains obtained as nonmagnetic at 1 A. Several Excel spreadsheets were formulated to conclude the chemical formulas of the various ilmenite alteration products. Based on the investigation and interpretation of the various data obtained, a new approach was proposed for the mechanisms of the ilmenite alteration processes. Furthermore, the conclusions of some previous studies are re-explained, and their unknown extending chemical formulas are well-defined and given.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS.

A large bulk sample of naturally highly concentrated beach black sand was collected from the Abu Khashaba beach area on the Mediterranean coast, 7 km east of Rosetta estuary. The sample represents the raw sand in a 4 km stretch with variable widths, from a few to 20 meters. The sand was manually scraped from the mantle to a depth ranging from 10-30 cm. This study investigated altered ilmenite grains obtained as a nonmagnetic fraction at 1 A. Most grains were very close to the relatively heavier magnetically altered ilmenite grains obtained at 1 A [25] but had relatively lighter colors. Using the difference in physical characteristics between the various economic minerals [16, 23-25], the collected surface naturally highly concentrated beach raw sand was processed using the following equipment and processes:

- Reading cross-belts magnetic separator to differentiate the raw sample into three fractions: a ferromagnetic, a bulk magnetic, and a bulk non-magnetic.
- Full-size Wilfley shaking tables for wet-gravity concentration of the bulk nonmagnetic fraction obtained.
- Carpc HP 167 high-tension roll-type electrostatic separator to treat the concentrate to obtain a bulk rutile conductor fraction and a bulk zircon nonconductor fraction.
- Carpc MIH 13-231-100 industrial high-intensity induced roll dry magnetic separator to separate the bulk rutile conductor fraction obtained.
- Frantz isodynamic magnetic separator: The three successive magnetic fractions obtained from the last treatment stage were mixed as a bulk magnetic fraction, composed of hematite, ilmeno-hematite, different varieties of magnetic primary rutile, and various grades of altered ilmenite grains, in addition to minor Cr-bearing and other magnetic minerals [16]. A relatively smaller representative sample of the bulk magnetic fraction was obtained and subjected to magnetic differentiation using the Frantz isodynamic magnetic separator with the following adjusted operating

conditions: longitudinal slope of 20° , side slope of 5° , feeding rate of 30 g/hour, and six different successive currents: 0.1, 0.2, 0.25, 0.35, 0.5, and 1 A. Six magnetic and one nonmagnetic fractions were obtained. This study investigated the altered ilmenite grains obtained in the individual nonmagnetic fraction separated at 1 A.

- Microscopic investigation: The altered ilmenite grains obtained from the separated individual nonmagnetic fraction was investigated using binocular and reflected microscopes.
- Microprobe analysis: The different altered ilmenite grains were examined in a Cameca SX-100 Electron Micro Probe Analyzer (EMPA), at the Institute of Mineralogy and Crystal Chemistry, Stuttgart University, Germany, equipped with three Wavelength Dispersive Spectrometers (WDS) and an Energy Dispersive Spectrometer (EDS). The whole surface of the polished sections was examined by Backscattered Electron (BSE) images so that grains with 10 μm size or even smaller obtained could be detected. The analytical conditions were: 15 kV accelerating voltage, 15 nA electron current, 180s counting time for each spot analyzed in the investigated grains, and a focused electron beam diameter of 1 to 4 μm . The following standards were used: diopside for Mg and Ca, albite for Na, corundum for Al, orthoclase for Si and K, rutile for Ti, rhodonite for Mn, Fe_2O_3 for Fe, Cr_2O_3 for Cr, V for V, and sphalerite for Zn. $K\alpha$ lines were used for each element analyzed. From the obtained nonmagnetic fraction, a definite number of grains were picked and polished for investigation using the microprobe.
- Philips PW 3710/31 XRD with automatic sample changer PW 1775, 21 positions, using a scintillation counter, Cu-target tube, Ni filter at 40 kV and 30 mA, connected to a computer using an X-40 diffraction program and ASTM cards for mineral identification.

All Excel spreadsheets used for the calculation of different molecular formulas of mineral phases, which is the final result of the essence and calculation algorithms, are available upon request [25, 26].

III. RESULTS

Six grains were investigated in the nonmagnetic fraction at 1 A. They were secondary rutile with TiO_2 , Fe_2O_3 , and total oxide sum ranging between 89.05-99.86 wt%, 0.03-8.8 wt%, and 94.55-100.76 wt%, respectively. Their chemical composition ranged from ferriiferous rutile and rutile with a considerable amount of molecular and/or structural water. An amazing altered leucoxene grain was detected during the investigation of some secondary rutile grains of grayish-white colors in the nonmagnetic fraction at 1 A, as shown in Figure 1 and Table I. In this grain, the TiO_2 content increased from 77.06 wt% in spot 1 to 90.78 wt% in spot 18, while the Fe_2O_3 content decreased from 5.37 wt% to 3.24 wt%, respectively. The increase in TiO_2 was 13.7 wt% while the corresponding decrease in Fe_2O_3 was 2.2 wt%. The decrease in Fe_2O_3 from spot 1 to spot 18 was very low and not negatively correlated with the relatively higher increase rate of TiO_2 . The Fe_2O_3

content does not have a definite tendency to increase or decrease through all the various spots analyzed in the grain, as shown in Table I. It is difficult to believe that the enrichment of TiO_2 content is due to such decreasing Fe_2O_3 content values. The identification for most economic minerals of the Egyptian black sand and other sand deposits using the XRD technique were explained in [16, 27]. The non magnetic altered ilmenite

grains at 1 A, were subjected to the XRD before and after roasting at 1100 °C for 1 hr. Before roasting, the XRD pattern of the grains was composed of only rutile but its diffraction lines were diffused indicating that it is of bad crystalline structure. After roasting, the XRD pattern of the sample gave the well defined pattern of rutile.

TABLE I. THE MICROPROBE CHEMICAL ANALYSES AND CORRESPONDING MOLECULAR FORMULAE OF THE ANALYZED SPOTS OF THE ALTERED GRAYISH-WHITE GRAIN OF FIGURE 1, SEPARATED AS NONMAGNETIC AT 1 A

Spot	SiO ₂	MgO	MnO	CaO	ZnO	Fe ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃	Cr ₂ O ₃	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	TiO ₂	O Total	OH%	H ₂ O%	N Total	Fe ₂	Ti ₃	Ox	OH _y	Lost Fe	Ti/(Ti+Fe)
1	0.66	0.07	0.06	0.19	0.00	5.37	0.61	0.19	0.08	0.07	77.06	84.36	27.89	14.77	99.13	0.32	3	3.95	5.05	1.68	0.90
2	0.70	0.07	0.00	0.19	0.00	5.29	0.58	0.18	0.24	0.19	77.11	84.54	27.81	14.73	99.27	0.34	3	3.96	5.04	1.66	0.90
3	0.74	0.09	0.04	0.32	0.00	4.68	0.55	0.12	0.33	0.16	78.07	85.10	28.22	14.95	100.05	0.32	3	3.90	5.10	1.68	0.90
4	0.69	0.07	0.01	0.05	0.00	2.94	0.25	0.04	0.03	0.05	79.18	83.32	30.77	16.30	99.61	0.18	3	3.55	5.45	1.82	0.94
5	0.60	0.07	0.01	0.29	0.00	4.83	0.58	0.17	0.12	0.06	83.53	90.27	28.87	15.29	105.56	0.28	3	3.81	5.19	1.72	0.92
6	0.57	0.06	0.03	0.21	0.00	4.58	0.61	0.16	0.09	0.04	84.42	90.75	29.24	15.49	106.23	0.26	3	3.76	5.24	1.74	0.92
7	0.61	0.07	0.02	0.23	0.00	3.73	0.46	0.17	0.04	0.03	85.77	91.12	30.10	15.94	107.06	0.21	3	3.64	5.36	1.79	0.93
8	0.60	0.08	0.00	0.19	0.00	3.95	0.54	0.17	0.03	0.04	84.27	89.85	29.81	15.79	105.64	0.22	3	3.68	5.32	1.78	0.93
9	0.67	0.07	0.00	0.19	0.00	4.34	0.55	0.23	0.07	0.04	85.04	91.22	29.36	15.55	106.77	0.25	3	3.74	5.26	1.75	0.92
10	0.55	0.03	0.00	0.15	0.00	3.61	0.53	0.17	0.02	0.02	85.59	90.66	30.30	16.05	106.71	0.20	3	3.61	5.39	1.80	0.94
11	0.66	0.04	0.01	0.19	0.00	4.00	0.55	0.20	0.03	0.02	86.36	92.05	29.81	15.79	107.84	0.22	3	3.68	5.32	1.78	0.93
12	1.11	0.18	0.00	0.07	0.00	4.99	0.56	0.06	0.03	0.05	86.01	93.06	28.57	15.13	108.19	0.28	3	3.86	5.14	1.72	0.91
13	0.17	0.02	0.00	0.06	0.00	4.73	0.34	0.12	0.04	0.04	87.74	93.24	30.28	16.04	109.28	0.20	3	3.60	5.40	1.80	0.94
14	0.22	0.07	0.01	0.07	0.00	4.97	0.34	0.09	0.11	0.03	87.86	93.77	29.96	15.87	109.63	0.22	3	3.64	5.36	1.78	0.93
15	0.29	0.03	0.00	0.13	0.00	4.47	0.36	0.09	0.08	0.10	88.02	93.57	30.22	16.01	109.58	0.21	3	3.61	5.39	1.79	0.93
16	0.16	0.03	0.01	0.03	0.00	4.09	0.06	0.04	0.01	0.03	89.12	93.56	31.22	16.53	110.09	0.15	3	3.46	5.54	1.85	0.95
17	0.51	0.04	0.03	0.11	0.00	3.39	0.35	0.07	0.05	0.02	90.59	95.16	30.98	16.41	111.57	0.17	3	3.51	5.49	1.83	0.95
18	0.10	0.01	0.00	0.05	0.00	3.24	0.09	0.03	0.04	0.02	90.78	94.36	31.94	16.92	111.28	0.12	3	3.37	5.63	1.88	0.96

Fig. 1. BSE image and chemical analysis spots of the altered-grayish white ilmenite grain, separated as non-magnetic at 1 A.

IV. DISCUSSION

The original total oxide sum (OT) was equal to 84.36 wt% in spot 1, 95.16 wt% in spot 17, and 94.4 wt% in spot 18. The OT of spot 18 is 10 wt% and 10.8 wt% greater than that in spots 1 and 17, respectively. The increase in OT in these spots essentially varies directly with the increase in TiO_2 content, while the differences in the other oxides analyzed are very low. Therefore, the enrichment of TiO_2 content for the different spots is most probably due to a loss of appreciable contents of structural and/or molecular water. After applying the PSR Excel spreadsheet, the first four spots (Figure 1, spots 1-4) appear to be LPSR, according to the results of Table I. In these

four spots, the new calculated total sum of the analyzed oxides (NT) ranged between 99.13 and 100.05 wt%, and the cationic iron content ranged between 0.18 and 0.34. Therefore, it is difficult for each of them to be a PSR, as it is mainly composed of an individual phase of TiO_2 in addition to the minor content of Fe_2O_3 . Some spots contain mixed individual phases for TiO_2 and Fe_2O_3 and seem falsely LPSR. The investigation of the BSE image of the grain reflects its composition of several similar units. Each unit is composed of various dark-light and black-white zones that may reflect differences in structural and/or molecular water content. These detected zones include black zones, gray zones, white zones, and mixed grayish-white zones. These zones also seem to be different in their content of TiO_2 , in addition to their content of structural and/or molecular water.

Investigating the relatively larger unit on the upper left of the grain showed that it was a combination of several small units that comprise the whole grain and in which the structural and/or molecular water begins to be removed. The relatively smaller unit at the lower right of the grain, which also attaches to the relatively larger unit at the upper left, is an indication of the aforementioned explanation. It seems that in each of these units of the detected grain, the contained structural water begins to differentiate between the various detected dark-light zones. After that, each similar dark or light zone of the various small units is connected to form one sector area, like that of the relatively larger unit at the upper left of the grain. A careful investigation of the chemical composition of the spots shows that the relatively lighter zones contain a relatively higher TiO_2 content and a relatively lower content of structural and/or molecular water. In the relatively darker zones, the TiO_2 content is relatively lower, while the structural and/or

molecular water content is relatively higher. The detected various dark-light zones of the relatively smaller units are not highly clear as those of the relatively larger unit at the upper left of the detected grain. It can be concluded that, in the white zones, most of the Ti-bearing phase is present mainly as oxide, while in the black zones, it is present mainly as oxyhydroxide. Due to the relatively lower iron content in the various analyzed spots, the presence of Fe³⁺-bearing phase as oxy, oxyhydroxide, or hydroxide phase does not greatly affect the enrichment of TiO₂ content. Additionally, the spots of the dark black zones analyzed in the outer region of the grain may have the possible characteristic lowest chemical composition of the LPSR formula component FeTi₃O₆(OH)₃ during the final stages of alteration.

The tetragonal rutile structure seems to be more compact than the hexagonal PSR structure. Therefore, it does not allow considerable content of OH⁻ inside it. Hence, the presence of Ti⁴⁺ and maybe Fe³⁺ as oxyhydroxide or hydroxide phases is not desired in appreciable amounts within the tetragonal rutile structure. In the white zones, the recorded water content seems to be largely molecular rather than structural, and vice versa in the black zones. Table II shows that the dehydroxylation process proceeds gradually with the transition from black zones to gray, grayish-white, and finally white zones. It is clear that there is a definite relation between both the analyzed contents of SiO₂ and Al₂O₃, and perhaps also CaO, and the recorded structural water content. In the grayish-white and white zones, these oxides are highly diminished, as shown in Table II.

TABLE II. CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF THE DIFFERENT ANALYZED SPOTS OF THE SEPARATED NON-MAGNETIC GRAIN OF FIGURE 1, SHOWING THE VARIOUS INVESTIGATED COLOURED ZONES AND THEIR CHEMICAL COMPOSITION RANGE CONTENTS OF TiO₂, Fe₂O₃ AND STRUCTURAL (STR)/MOLECULAR (MOL) WATER

Spot	Zone Type	TiO ₂	Fe ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	CaO	Cr ₂ O ₃	MgO	MnO	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	Total	TiO ₂ content range	Fe ₂ O ₃ content range	STR & MOL H ₂ O content range
1	Outer black	77.1	5.4	0.7	0.6	0.19	0.19	0.07	0.06	0.08	0.07	84.4	77.1-78.1	4.7-5.4	15.6-14.9
2		77.1	5.3	0.7	0.6	0.19	0.18	0.07	0.00	0.24	0.19	84.5			
3		78.1	4.7	0.7	0.6	0.32	0.12	0.09	0.04	0.33	0.16	85.1			
4	Inner black	79.2	2.9	0.7	0.3	0.05	0.04	0.07	0.01	0.03	0.05	83.3	79.2	2.9	16.7
5	Outer grey	83.5	4.8	0.6	0.6	0.29	0.17	0.07	0.01	0.12	0.06	90.3	83.5-85.8	3.7-4.8	9.7-8.9
6		84.4	4.6	0.6	0.6	0.21	0.16	0.06	0.03	0.09	0.04	90.8			
7		85.8	3.7	0.6	0.5	0.23	0.17	0.07	0.02	0.04	0.03	91.1			
8	Inner grey	84.3	4.0	0.6	0.5	0.19	0.17	0.08	0.00	0.03	0.04	89.9	84.3-86.4	3.6-4.3	10.1-7.9
9		85.0	4.3	0.7	0.6	0.19	0.23	0.07	0.00	0.07	0.04	91.2			
10		85.6	3.6	0.6	0.5	0.15	0.17	0.03	0.00	0.02	0.02	90.7			
11		86.4	4.0	0.7	0.6	0.19	0.20	0.04	0.01	0.03	0.02	92.1			
12	Outer Greish white	86.0	5.0	1.1	0.6	0.07	0.06	0.18	0.00	0.03	0.05	93.1	86-88	4.5-5	6.9-6.2
13		87.7	4.7	0.2	0.3	0.06	0.12	0.02	0.00	0.04	0.04	93.2			
14		87.9	5.0	0.2	0.3	0.07	0.09	0.07	0.01	0.11	0.03	93.8			
15		88	4.5	0.3	0.4	0.13	0.09	0.03	0.00	0.08	0.10	93.6			
16	Inner white	89.1	4.1	0.2	0.1	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.03	93.6	89.1-90.8	3.2-4.1	6.4-4.8
17		90.6	3.4	0.5	0.4	0.11	0.07	0.04	0.03	0.05	0.02	95.2			
18		90.8	3.2	0.1	0.1	0.05	0.03	0.01	0.00	0.04	0.02	94.4			

The presence of more than one iron oxidation state (Fe²⁺, Fe³⁺) contained in ilmenite (FeTiO₃ or Fe₃Ti₃O₉) may be the reason for the alteration into various products. Hence, under definite environmental conditions, ilmenite is unstable due to the oxidation of Fe²⁺ to Fe³⁺ inside its structure, which will be associated with the partial leaching of some iron content and the formation of another unstable phase called leached ilmenite. The leaching of one-third of the ferric iron content produces another mineral phase, called PSR Fe³⁺₂Ti₃O₉, which contains several micro-fissures, cracks, and pores that are formed not only during the leaching stage of ilmenite but possibly also during the various stages of weathering, transportation, deposition, and/or diagenesis in some ilmenite deposits. Additionally, such fissures and cracks may be due to selective alteration processes (e.g. dissolution) under definite environmental conditions for some impurities (inclusions) or exsolved intergrowths of various mineral components occurring in definite parts and orientations for many of the non-homogeneous ilmenite grains. However, the presence of such microstructures of ilmenite grains may increase the activity of molecular water and the chances of oxidation and alteration of ilmenite.

According to [25-26], considering that the chemical formula of ilmenite is Fe₃Ti₃O₉, the contents of TiO₂, FeO, and Fe₂O₃ in the leached ilmenite formed range between 51.39-59.19 wt%, 39.84-0.02 wt%, and 3-37.02 wt%, respectively. Fe²⁺ ranged between 0 and 2.46, while Fe³⁺ ranged between 0.17 and 1.94. The Ti/(Ti+Fe) ratio ranged between 0.51 and 0.6, almost the same as [28], which gives ranges between 0.5 and 0.6. The Fe/Ti ratio ranged from 0.91 to 0.67, which is different from the given by [29] that stated that the molar ratio Fe/Ti for ilmenite is 1.02, decreases to approximately 0.84 for pseudo-ilmenite and 0.64 for PSR. NT ranged between 90.24 and 101.27 wt%. Most of the values were much lower than 100 wt%, reflecting the role of molecular water in the process of ilmenite oxidation into leached ilmenite and also the following alteration stages in the PSR and LPSR phases.

According to [30-31], oxidation occurs by water or steam in the absence of air. With the aid of small amounts of HCl (as a catalyst), siderite (FeCO₃) is oxidized to Fe(OH)₃ at 150°C, and magnetite becomes Fe₂O₃ at 200°C. These are probably not the minimum temperatures at which these reactions become noticeable. The following two concurrent equations for ilmenite alteration were suggested by [32]:

Anodic oxidation mechanism:

Cathodic half-cell reaction:

According to them, the formed (OH^-) readily complexes with Fe^{3+} of (1) to form goethite. By neglecting Mn^{2+} in (1) and multiplying (2) in (3), the last two equations can be reformulated as follows:

However, by summation of (3) and (4) we get:

The last equation is the same as the first equation obtained from the model of [33], where both Fe^{3+} and OH^- combine to give $Fe^{3+}(OH)_3$, in addition to the formed PSR ($Fe_2^{3+}Ti_3O_9$). This reaction operates in a saturated, mildly acidic oxygenated water environment below the water table [10, 33]. If the produced $3OH^-$ of (4) is complexed with the ferric iron of PSR $Fe_2^{3+}Ti_3O_9$ and then bonded with it replacing $3O_2^-$ by losing another Fe^{3+} , then:

Therefore, by the summation of (3), (4), and (6):

The situation in (7) requires that Fe^{3+} does not form $Fe(OH)_3$ in the products of (5). Hence, hematite is formed instead of $Fe^{3+}(OH)_3$ or goethite. After that, hematite is directly leached or can be changed to goethite and then leached. The exsolved hematite inside the titanhematite-ferrilmenite exsolved intergrown grains of the Egyptian black sand is altered to goethite, which is lost, leaving the titanhematite lamella as empty voids or pits. Meanwhile, most of the ferrilmenite component of the grain remains unchanged. This explanation may be responsible for some recorded Egyptian beach ilmenite varieties known as pitted ilmenite [18], skeletal ilmenite [20, 34], or microporous ilmenite [16]. However, regardless of the occurrence of (6) and (7), the PSR phase obtained from (5) appears to be altered into another PSR phase by losing ferric iron and replacing oxygen with hydroxide. When one Fe^{3+} is lost, three O^{2-} are replaced by three OH^- due to water hydrolysis to achieve the electrical neutralization of the new LPSR phase obtained. The combination of hydration with oxidation causes an increase in water content together with a linear decrease in Fe^{2+} iron content in the composition region from ilmenite to PSR and encompasses hydrated (leached) ilmenite as shown in [11, 35].

The further removal of Fe^{3+} beyond the PSR composition is followed by the breakdown into TiO_2 and Fe_2O_3 . This process proceeds through a leaching and reprecipitation mechanism in a mildly reducing acidic solution [33]. According to [36], the model of [33] has several weaknesses. The two model's reactions require different environments to proceed. The first requires an oxidizing one and the second a reducing one, with its reliance on reducing conditions in near-surface conditions. However, within the PSR composition range (60-71% TiO_2), the water content increased from ~2 to 4.5 wt% with decreasing iron oxide content [37], suggesting that the intermediate alteration phases comprised mixtures of TiO_2 with iron hydroxides.

A. The New Approach of Ilmenite Alteration

At the end of the leached ilmenite phase, most of the ferrous iron Fe^{2+} is oxidized into ferric, where one-third of the ilmenite's iron content is removed and another definite chemical formula phase is formed. This new phase is called PSR: $Fe_2^{3+}Ti_3O_9$.

In the obtained PSR formula, the TiO_2 content almost equals 60 wt % and the remaining 40 wt % is mainly for Fe_2O_3 and other associated oxides. The given values of the $Ti/(Ti+Fe)$ ratios for PSR vary across studies: 0.5-0.7 [38], 0.57-0.7 [9], 0.6-0.7 [28], 0.6 [39], 0.6-0.79 or 0.80 [11]. The lower chemical composition formula limit of PSR is $Fe_2Ti_3O_9$ [33], $Fe_{1.5}Ti_3O_{7.5}(OH)_{1.5}$ [28], while [9] considered the average composition of LPSR as $FeTi_3O_6(OH)_3$, and the lower stability limit lies around 0.6 mol% Fe or slightly higher, as related to 3 mol% Ti.

According to [25-26], in the analyzed spots of PSR and LPSR, the contents of TiO_2 and Fe_2O_3 range between 56.76 and 86.56 wt%, and 37.3 and 6.68 wt%, respectively. The $Ti/(Ti+Fe)$ ratio ranges between 0.60-0.88. The PSR and LPSR chemical formulas are as follows: $Fe_{2.01-0.42}Ti_3O_{9.4.23}(OH)_{0.4.77}$. Only eight analyzed spots have cationic iron ranges between 0.28 and 0.38, while 16 analyzed spots have cationic iron ranges between 0.42 and 0.49. Investigating the backscattered electron images of grains with spots that have cationic iron ranges between 0.42 and 0.49 ensures the existence of some survived LPSR in association with the formed rutile. Then, the lowest cationic iron content of the survived LPSR phase is between 0.42-0.5 with a corresponding molecular formula of $Fe_{0.5-0.42}Ti_3O_{4.26-4.5}(OH)_{4.5-4.74}$. In other words, when the iron content decreases below 0.5, the structure of the present LPSR phase begins to collapse. The complete collapse of the LPSR phase structure into an individual TiO_2 phase appears to be at any value within the range of 0.5-0.4 of iron content. The given values of the $Ti/(Ti+Fe)$ ratio for LPSR are different between studies. In [9], it was found between 0.72 and 0.8, and it ranged between 0.79 or 0.8 and 0.9 in [11]. In [10], it was reported that the analyses of HPR, in the same area studied with [11], had a $Ti/(Ti+Fe)$ ratio of 0.8-0.85, representing 3.3 wt%, while those in the range of 0.85-0.9 represented 2.13 wt% of the total analyses performed. According to [25], when the TiO_2 content of the investigated LPSR phase spots reaches values in the region of 68-70 wt%, the mechanism of alteration seems to be changing. The comparison between OT and NT after applying

the constructed PSR spreadsheet shows that the calculated structural water contents of the analyzed spots are incorrect. In other words, not all the analyzed TiO_2 of the spot is contained in the PSR/LPSR phase. There are other individual phases of TiO_2 and/or Fe_2O_3 , since the two main oxides contained in the analyzed spot most probably separate from the LPSR phase [25].

Taking into account the PSR phase formula $\text{Fe}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_9$, when losing a definite amount (x) of Fe^{3+} another formula phase is formed. It is called LPSR $\text{FeTi}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_3$ (8) and contains $(9-3x)\text{O}^{2-}$ and $(3x)\text{OH}^-$. In this LPSR formula, the TiO_2 , Fe_2O_3 , and structural water contents are equal to 69.17, 23.05, and 7.79 wt%, respectively. It was detected that during the alteration of the PSR phase $\text{Fe}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_9$ to the LPSR phase $\text{FeTi}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_3$, there is no change in the alteration mechanism. Most of the chemical analyses of the investigated LPSR spots lie within the range of these two chemical formulas, which give acceptable results on applying the constructed PSR-LPSR spreadsheets. The last chemical formula phase, $\text{FeTi}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_3$, is considered the most stable lowest iron LPSR structure for its content of OH^- . In this LPSR formula, the OH/O ratio is equal to 0.5. Then, each of the three Ti atoms seems to be stable with this ratio of surrounding O and OH. When the number of O anions becomes less than six, their corresponding negative charges become less than 12, e.g., in the LPSR formula $\text{Fe}_{0.83}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{5.5}(\text{OH})_{3.5}$, the three Ti atoms seem to become unstable. In this LPSR formula phase, losing a definite amount (x) of Fe^{3+} (for example $x=1/6$ or 0.17 Fe^{3+}), another LPSR formula phase is formed containing $(6-3x)\text{O}$ and $(3+3x)\text{OH}^-$:

The newly formed LPSR phase starts to rearrange gradually and slowly to maintain its stability. However, according to the lost amount of Fe^{3+} from the LPSR phase $\text{FeTi}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_3$, several scenarios are expected to occur. The prevailing surrounding environmental conditions affect the deposit, including altered ilmenite grains such as water activity, pH/Eh, and effective time, which can govern the loss rate of Fe^{3+} outside the LPSR structure phase. Therefore, three scenarios are proposed for the lost content of Ti-oxyhydroxide from the LPSR formula structure. Each of them includes several probable cases to achieve the target, as shown in Figures 2-7. On the dehydroxylation of clay minerals, it was stated in [40] that due to greater stiffness, thicker crystallites require more energy to dehydroxylate, which also requires opening of the interlayer [41-42], therefore, there is a need for more thermal energy or higher water pressure provided to rehydroxylate than thinner crystallites. According to [11], there is a more extensive network of nanopores in the HPSR than in the PSR. Then, in the various LPSR alteration scenarios, the alteration processes are gradual and slow and occur on a nano-alteration scale which introduces highly thinner crystallites and facilitates the alteration changes.

1) Scenario A

With the loss of $1/6 \text{ Fe}^{3+}$, then $3 \times 1/6$ of oxygen, namely a half O^{2-} , will be replaced by a half OH^- and another LPSR-phase other than $\text{FeTi}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_3$ will be formed, which is $\text{Fe}_{0.83}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{5.5}(\text{OH})_{3.5}$. Figure 2 shows the contents of TiO_2 , Fe_2O_3 , and structural molecular water in the obtained LPSR phase. However, the obtained LPSR phase structure seems to be relatively less stable and will try to resume the most stable lowest iron LPSR-phase of $\text{FeTi}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_3$. To achieve the target, four cases may be postulated to occur A1, A2, A3, and A4, as shown in Figure 2. Considering the partial leaching of the altered LPSR $\text{FeTi}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_3$ of case A1, the content of the separated individual Ti-phase, $1/2(\text{TiO}_2)$ corresponds to three folds of the partially leached LPSR-phase content $1/6(\text{FeTi}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_3)$, and the remaining LPSR phase is $5/6(\text{FeTi}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_3)$. In case A2, the separated individual Ti-phase is TiO_2 , which corresponds to three folds the content of the partially leached LPSR-phase content which is $2/6(\text{FeTi}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_3)$, and the remaining LPSR phase is $4/6(\text{FeTi}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_3)$. In case A3, the separated individual Ti-phase is $1.5(\text{TiO}_2)$, which corresponds to three folds the content of the partially leached LPSR-phase content, which is $3/6(\text{FeTi}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_3)$, and the remaining LPSR phase is $3/6(\text{FeTi}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_3)$. In case A4, the separated individual Ti-phase is $2(\text{TiO}_2)$, which corresponds to three folds the content of the partially leached LPSR-phase content, which is $4/6(\text{FeTi}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_3)$, and the remaining LPSR-phase is $2/6(\text{FeTi}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_3)$. In case A1, only a definite amount of Ti-oxyhydroxide will be removed from the LPSR phase, as there is no loss of other additional amounts of Fe^{3+} , as in cases A2, A3, and A4 to adjust the anionic structure of the LPSR obtained. In case A1, the unstable composite alteration phase produced $\text{Fe}_{0.83}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_{2.5}$, and the false ratio of $\text{Ti}/(\text{Ti}+\text{Fe})$ is equal to 0.78. If the available surrounding environment conditions are suitable for leaching a relatively higher Fe^{3+} content (e.g., $2/6\text{Fe}^{3+}$) of the most stable lowest iron LPSR $\text{FeTi}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_3$, then another expected scenario is formed with another unstable LPSR chemical formula, scenario B.

2) Scenario B

In this scenario, the removed Fe^{3+} content outside the most stable lowest iron LPSR-phase is $2/6\text{Fe}^{3+}$. Another unstable LPSR chemical formula is obtained $\text{Fe}_{0.67}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_5(\text{OH})_4$, containing 72.84, 16.21, and 10.75 wt % of TiO_2 , Fe_2O_3 , and structural molecular water, respectively. This obtained LPSR-phase structure seems to be relatively less stable and will try to resume the most stable lowest iron LPSR $\text{FeTi}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_3$ phase. To achieve the target, the two cases B1 and B2 of Figure 3 are expected to occur, which can also be obtained by losing $1/6\text{Fe}^{3+}$ from the unstable phase obtained in case A1 $\text{Fe}_{0.83}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{5.5}(\text{OH})_{3.5}$. In the B1 and B2 cases, the unstable composite alteration phase produced contains 0.67 cationic iron, and the calculated false ratio of $\text{Ti}/(\text{Ti}+\text{Fe})$ equals 0.82. When not only Ti-oxyhydroxide is removed but also $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$, then another four cases, B3, B4, B5, and B6, of Scenario B are expected to occur, as shown in Figure 4. In all these cases of scenario B, the TiO_2 phase corresponds to three folds of the leached fraction of the original $\text{FeTi}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_3$. In the two cases B1 and B2, the TiO_2 produced corresponds to $3 \times 2/6(\text{FeTi}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_3)$. In the cases B3 and B4, the $1.5(\text{TiO}_2)$ produced corresponds to $3 \times 3/6(\text{FeTi}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_3)$, while in B5

and B6, the $2(\text{TiO}_2)$ produced corresponds to $3 \times 4/6(\text{FeTi}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_3)$, as shown in Figures 3 and 4.

Fig. 2. Scenario A including the cases A1, A2, A3, and A4, and their corresponding final products. The label numbers from 1 to 6 in this and the following figures are for the following: 1- The chemical composition of the remaining individual LPSR phase, 2- the mixed chemical composition of the obtained two individual LPSR and titanium dioxide phases, 3- the recalculated mixed chemical composition of the obtained two individual LPSR and titanium dioxide phases after removing only of the produced Fe(OH)₃ phase, 4- the recalculated mixed chemical composition of the obtained two individual LPSR and titanium dioxide phases after the removing the produced Fe(OH)₃ and mol water, 5- the true (Ti/Ti+Fe) ratio, and 6- the false (Ti/Ti+Fe) ratio.

Fig. 3. Scenario B including the two probable cases B1 and B2, and their corresponding final products.

Fig. 4. Scenario B including the other four probable cases B3, B4, B5, and B6, and their corresponding final products.

3) Scenario C

If the Fe³⁺ leached from the most stable LPSR phase is 3/6, then another unstable LPSR chemical formula is obtained (Fe_{0.5}Ti₃O_{4.5}(OH)_{4.5}), as shown in Figure 5. The same result can be obtained by losing 1/6 Fe³⁺ from the unstable phase obtained from B1 or B2 (Fe_{0.67}Ti₃O₅(OH)₄). Figure 5 shows the contents of the different components of the new LPSR phase when losing 3/6Fe³⁺. This LPSR structure appears to be relatively less stable and will try to resume the most stable lowest iron LPSR phase FeTi₃O₆(OH)₃. Hence, a definite content of an individual Ti-oxyhydroxide phase will be separated, Ti_{1.5}O_{1.5}(OH)₃ and all cases C1, C2, and C3 can be obtained. In these cases, the unstable composite alteration phases produced contain 0.50 cationic iron, and the false ratio of Ti/(Ti+Fe) is 0.86. If the leached Fe³⁺ content outside the most stable LPSR phase is 4/6 instead of 3/6, then another unstable LPSR formula is obtained (Fe_{2/6}Ti₃O₄(OH)₅), as shown in Figure 6. However, the same result can also be obtained by losing 1/6 of Fe³⁺ from the unstable phase obtained from C1, C2, or C3 (Fe_{3/6}Ti₃O_{4.5}(OH)_{4.5}). The new LPSR phase in this case has the different component contents shown in Figure 6. The obtained LPSR-phase structure Fe_{2/6}Ti₃O₄(OH)₅ appears to be relatively less stable and will try to resume the most stable lowest iron LPSR phase FeTi₃O₆(OH)₃. In this case, the separated Ti-oxyhydroxide content must be Ti₂O₂(OH)₄, and cases C4, C5, C6, and C7 are expected to occur (Figure 6). In these cases, the unstable composite alteration phases produced contain 0.33 cationic iron and the false ratio of Ti/(Ti+Fe) is 0.90. However, if it was supposed that the separated Ti-oxyhydroxide content is Ti₂O_{2.5}(OH)₃, then some iron content, 1/6(Fe (OH)₃), must also be removed to obtain finally mixed products composed of the relatively most stable lowest iron LPSR phase FeTi₃O₆(OH)₃, in addition to a separated individual TiO₂ or Ti-oxyhydroxide phase in a ratio of 1:3. Then, another three cases, C8, C9, and C10, of scenario C are expected to occur, as shown

in Figure 7. In all 10 cases of scenario C, the TiO₂ produced corresponds to three folds the leached fraction of the original FeTi₃O₆(OH)₃ shown in Figures 5-7. Investigating the 20 individual mineralogical phases from the three suggested scenarios gives the data shown in Table III, where True Ratio (TR) is the ratio corresponding only to both Ti and Fe contents in the actual remaining LPSR component phase. The False Ratio (FR) corresponds to the total contents of Ti and Fe of all the contained phases as a final product, in all LPSR and Ti-oxide or Ti-oxyhydroxide individual phases. That is, all of the analyzed TiO₂ wt% of the detected spot is considered. Table IV shows the weight percentages of the various chemical components of the final composite products obtained for the 20 cases of the three scenarios, after removing Fe(OH)₃ produced with or without the associated molecular water.

Investigating Tables III and IV shows that some of the final products obtained in the different cases are similar, where only the associated individual molecular water is different. The 20 phases obtained can be reduced to only 10 alteration phases. The 10 cases that will be considered are the A1 case of Scenario A, B1-B2 cases of Scenario B, and C1-C7 cases of Scenario C. In these chosen 10 cases, only unstable immobile titanium oxyhydroxide is separated from the LPSR phase and there is no change in the iron content. It is difficult to accept that other definite amounts of Fe(OH)₃ can be separated in association with the separated amount of Ti-oxyhydroxide (cases A2-A4, B3-B6, and C8-C10). In the 10 chosen cases, the TR ratios were 0.75, which is the same as the most stable lowest iron LPSR phase FeTi₃O₆(OH)₃, while the FR ratios are different, as shown in Tables III and IV since they range from 0.78 to 0.90. The values of the Ti/(Ti+Fe) ratios for leucoxene vary between studies. This ratio ranged between 0.7-0.9 [38] and 0.7-1 [28]. The Fe/Ti ratio of the given HPSR was 0.33 [39], which corresponds to FeTi₃O₆(OH)₃. On the other hand, in [11], it was stated that HPSR had a sum of (O+OH) equal to

7.5 or 8. Therefore, the ratio (O+OH)/Ti in this HPSR was 2.5-2.67, not 3, as in $Fe_2Ti_3O_9$ or $FeTi_3O_6(OH)_3$.

One of the most amazing results is the C2 and C3 cases of scenario C. Multiplying each of the two final products obtained, including also the separated molecular water in (2), the following two chemical formulas are obtained, respectively:

Each of these two formulas is similar to one of the two suggested formulas of HPR given in [11].

Fig. 5. Scenario C including the three probable cases C1, C2, and C3, and their corresponding final products.

Fig. 6. Scenario C including the four probable cases C4, C5, C6, and C7, and their corresponding final products.

Fig. 7. Scenario C including the three probable cases C8,C9, and C10, and their corresponding final products.

TABLE III. INDIVIDUAL MINERALOGICAL PHASES PRODUCED FROM EACH DIFFERENT SCENARIO PHASE CASE, THEIR CORRESPONDING ANION CONTENTS, MOLECULAR WATER, AND BOTH OF TRUE/FALSE TI/(TI+FE) RATIOS

Scenario cases	The final product of the mixed individual phases	Molecular water content	Number of O ²⁻ anions for composite mineral phases	Number of OH ⁻ anions for composite mineral phases	Total number of anions; Σ O, OH	Ti/(Ti+Fe)	
						True	False
A1	5/6[FeTi ₃ O ₆ (OH) ₃], 0.5TiO ₂	0.5 H ₂ O	6 O	2.5OH	8.5	0.75	0.78
A2	4/6[FeTi ₃ O ₆ (OH) ₃], TiO ₂	0.5 H ₂ O	6 O	2OH	8	0.75	0.82
A3	3/6[FeTi ₃ O ₆ (OH) ₃], 1.5 TiO ₂	0.5 H ₂ O	6 O	1.5OH	7.5	0.75	0.86
A4	2/6[FeTi ₃ O ₆ (OH) ₃], 2TiO ₂	0.5 H ₂ O	6 O	1 OH	7	0.75	0.90
B1	4/6[FeTi ₃ O ₆ (OH) ₃], Ti _{1.5} O ₂ (OH)	0.5 H ₂ O	5.5 O	3 OH	8.5	0.75	0.82
B2	4/6[FeTi ₃ O ₆ (OH) ₃], TiO ₂	H ₂ O	6 O	2 OH	8	0.75	0.82
B3	3/6[FeTi ₃ O ₆ (OH) ₃], Ti _{1.5} O _{2.5} (OH)	0.5 H ₂ O	5.5 O	2.5 OH	8	0.75	0.86
B4	3/6[FeTi ₃ O ₆ (OH) ₃], 1.5TiO ₂	H ₂ O	6 O	1.5 OH	7.5	0.75	0.86
B5	2/6[FeTi ₃ O ₆ (OH) ₃], 2TiO ₂	H ₂ O	6 O	1 OH	7	0.75	0.90
B6	2/6[FeTi ₃ O ₆ (OH) ₃], Ti ₂ O _{3.5} (OH)	0.5 H ₂ O	5.5 O	2 OH	7.5	0.75	0.90
C1	3/6[FeTi ₃ O ₆ (OH) ₃], Ti _{1.5} O ₂ (OH) ₂	0.5 H ₂ O	5 O	3.5 OH	8.5	0.75	0.86
C2	3/6[FeTi ₃ O ₆ (OH) ₃], Ti _{1.5} O _{2.5} (OH)	H ₂ O	5.5 O	2.5 OH	8	0.75	0.86
C3	3/6[FeTi ₃ O ₆ (OH) ₃], 1.5TiO ₂	1.5 H ₂ O	6 O	1.5 OH	7.5	0.75	0.86
C4	2/6[FeTi ₃ O ₆ (OH) ₃], Ti ₂ O _{2.5} (OH) ₃	0.5 H ₂ O	4.5 O	4 OH	8.5	0.75	0.90
C5	2/6[FeTi ₃ O ₆ (OH) ₃], Ti ₂ O ₃ (OH) ₂	H ₂ O	5 O	3 OH	8	0.75	0.90
C6	2/6[FeTi ₃ O ₆ (OH) ₃], Ti ₂ O _{3.5} (OH)	1.5 H ₂ O	5.5 O	2 OH	7.5	0.75	0.90
C7	2/6[FeTi ₃ O ₆ (OH) ₃], 2TiO ₂	2 H ₂ O	6 O	1 OH	7	0.75	0.90
C8	2/6[FeTi ₃ O ₆ (OH) ₃], Ti ₂ O ₃ (OH) ₂	0.5 H ₂ O	5 O	3 OH	8	0.75	0.90
C9	2/6[FeTi ₃ O ₆ (OH) ₃], Ti ₂ O _{3.5} (OH)	H ₂ O	5.5 O	2 OH	7.5	0.75	0.90
C10	2/6[FeTi ₃ O ₆ (OH) ₃], 2TiO ₂	1.5 H ₂ O	6 O	1 OH	7	0.75	0.90

However, each of the two formulas of cases C2 and C3 of Scenario C is considered to be composed of the relatively most stable lowest iron LPSR phase FeTi₃O₆(OH)₃, in addition to the separated individual TiO₂ or Ti-oxhydroxide phase in a ratio equal to 1:3, respectively, and the presence of one or 1.5 of individual molecular water molecules. Based on chemical and structural analyses of individual HPSR grains, in [11], a

composition range was calculated for HPR between approximately Fe³⁺Ti₆O₁₂(OH)₃.3H₂O and Fe³⁺Ti₆O₁₁(OH)₅.2H₂O, reporting that the full extent of the composition range is unknown and the molecular water is nonstructural, probably absorbed on the surfaces of nanoscale domains of the mineral and associated with impurities in micropores (as H₂O and/or OH). Dividing the two formulas

given in [11] by 2, the composition will range between $\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_{1.5}\cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{5.5}(\text{OH})_{2.5}\cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, respectively.

These two chemical formulas do not correspond to the PSR structure despite the XRD patterns of the PSR for the studied HPSR grains obtained. The anionic lattice structure is not the same as the well-defined PSR $\text{Fe}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_9$ or $\text{Fe}_{2-n}\text{Ti}_3(\text{O}_{9-3n}, \text{OH}_{3n})$, where $\text{O}+\text{OH}=9$. It appears that these two formulas of [11] are mixtures between a survivable LPSR and an amorphous TiO_2 phase or the most probably epitaxial growth of the triple rutile

on the hexagonal-packed anion layers of a collapsed part of a preexisting LPSR. Therefore, such an individual TiO_2 phase is either structureless or has the same PSR structure as HPSR. The disappearance of the micro- or crypto-crystalline TiO_2 -phase in the XRD pattern of the detected HPR grains of [11] does not mean the absence of an additional individual TiO_2 phase with the HPR structure. The presence of individual TiO_2 content in HPR grains of [11] explains why some HPSR grains were obtained in the non-magnetic fraction at 11 kilogauss, although their grain sizes are $+125 \mu$, like the majority of the magnetic HPR grains.

TABLE IV. WEIGHT PERCENTAGES OF THE CHEMICAL COMPONENTS FOR THE FINAL COMPOSITE CHEMICAL PRODUCTS OF ALL CASES OF THE THREE PROPOSED SCENARIOS WITH AND WITHOUT THE ASSOCIATED INDIVIDUAL MOLECULAR WATER

Scenario cases	The final obtained composite chemical product	Range of TiO_2 content wt %	Range of Fe_2O_3 content wt %	Range of structural water content wt %	Range of molecular water content wt %
A1	$\text{Fe}_{5/6}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_{2.5} + 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	70.96-72.89	19.7-20.23	6.66-6.84	2.67—0
A2	$\text{Fe}_{2/3}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_2 + 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	74.96-77.08	16.66-17.13	5.62-5.78	2.82-0
A3	$\text{Fe}_{1/2}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_{1.5} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	79.36-81.77	13.21-13.62	4.47-4.61	2.98-0
A4	$\text{Fe}_{1/3}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH}) + 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	84.31-87.08	9.3-9.67	3.17-3.28	3.17-0
B1	$\text{Fe}_{2/3}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{5.5}(\text{OH})_3 + 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	72.84-74.88	16.21-16.66	8.2-8.43	2.75-0
B2	$\text{Fe}_{2/3}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	72.84-77.07	16.21-17.15	5.48-5.8	5.47-0
B3	$\text{Fe}_{1/2}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{5.5}(\text{OH})_{2.5} + 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	77-79.35	12.83-13.21	7.23-7.44	2.96-0
B4	$\text{Fe}_{1/2}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_{1.5} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	77-81.78	12.83-13.62	4.33-4.6	5.78-0
B5	$\text{Fe}_{1/3}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH}) + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	81.74-87.06	9.09-9.67	3.09-3.29	6.14-0
B6	$\text{Fe}_{1/3}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{5.5}(\text{OH})_2 + 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	81.74-84.3	9.09-9.36	6.15-6.34	3.05-0
C1	$\text{Fe}_{1/2}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_5(\text{OH})_{3.5} + 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	74.88-77.05	12.47-12.83	9.84-10.13	2.81-0
C2	$\text{Fe}_{1/2}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{5.5}(\text{OH})_{2.5} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	74.88-79.37	12.47-13.22	7.03-7.45	5.62-0
C3	$\text{Fe}_{1/2}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_{1.5} + 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	74.88-81.77	12.47-13.62	4.22-4.61	8.43-0
C4	$\text{Fe}_{1/3}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{4.5}(\text{OH})_4 + 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	77-79.31	8.54-8.8	11.58-11.93	2.89-0
C5	$\text{Fe}_{1/3}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_5(\text{OH})_3 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	77-81.7	8.54-9.06	8.68-9.21	5.78-0
C6	$\text{Fe}_{1/3}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{5.5}(\text{OH})_2 + 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	77-84.32	8.54-9.35	5.79-6.34	8.67-0
C7	$\text{Fe}_{1/3}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH}) + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	77-87.09	8.54-9.66	2.89-3.27	11.56-0
C8	$\text{Fe}_{1/3}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_5(\text{OH})_3 + 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	79.3-81.7	8.8-9.08	8.93-9.21	2.98-0
C9	$\text{Fe}_{1/3}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{5.5}(\text{OH})_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	79.3-84.31	8.8-9.35	5.96-6.34	5.95-0
C10	$\text{Fe}_{1/3}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH}) + 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	79.3-87.09	8.8-9.67	3-3.28	8.9-0

Furthermore, the hydrated phase proposed in [43] does not conform to the PSR formula $\text{Fe}^{3+}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_9$ [10]. Multiplying the equation of [43] by 1.5 or 3, the obtained phase is well accepted as it extended the LPSR phase as follows:

Then, by multiplying by 1.5:

The equation in [43] is considered a definitive extended LPSR phase due to the alteration of ilmenite. According to the prevailing surrounding environmental conditions, if the separated Ti-bearing phase is formed as a micro- or crypto-crystalline randomly distributed phase with the remaining LPSR, the structure will be weakened and collapsed, giving what is called leucoxene. This process can occur in any early stage of the LPSR phases, followed by the LPSR phase of $\text{FeTi}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_3$. According to [33, 44], after the breakdown of PSR $\text{Fe}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_9$, rutile is developed as oriented aggregates by epitaxial growth in the hexagonal close-packed anion layers of ilmenite. Therefore, rutile is present in a triply twinned

arrangement in altered ilmenite [33, 44]. Then, if the separated Ti-bearing phase is crystallized in the triply twinned rutile phase structure, which seems to have the same XRD pattern as PSR, with the survived remaining LPSR and upon the hexagonal close-packed anion layers of the PSR structure, it will support the structure, and the HPSR can be formed with various successive chemical formula structures.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study concluded and illustrated a well-defined new approach to the alteration of ilmenite and the formation of several LPSR phases. The $\text{Fe}^{3+}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_9$ PSR formula phase is relatively more stable than other PSR and LPSR phases. Although the $\text{Fe}^{3+}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_3$ LPSR phase is unstable, it is considered the most stable lowest iron LPSR phase. When the LPSR formula reaches $\text{FeTi}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_3$, having almost 69% TiO_2 content, the PSR structure starts to lose some of its structural water, but at a very slow rate. Losing additional Fe^{3+} content from this PSR structure, the number of O^{2-} decreases to less than 6, while the number of OH increases above 3. The structure of the obtained LPSR phase becomes somewhat unstable but does not break down suddenly. When the number of O^{2-} becomes much lower than 6, the loss rate of structural water becomes rapid by removing the definite contents of Ti-

and/or Fe- oxyhydroxide phases. The balance between the removal of additional Fe^{3+} from the LPSR formula $\text{FeTi}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_3$ and the loss rate of structural water may be governed by the prevailing physical conditions of the surrounding environment, especially the activity of water. When approaching the formula $\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{4.5}(\text{OH})_{4.5}$, at least 1.5 water molecules, associated with a definite Ti-phase, are removed from the structure of the PSR. At these conditions, the structure of the LPSR formula becomes highly unstable, collapses, and the constituent atoms, especially the most abundant Ti atoms, start to rearrange and recrystallize into a more stable form, most probably rutile.

During the proceeding of the last explained mechanism, three scenarios were obtained. Each of them includes several obtained cases of different molecular formulas for LPSR. A total of 20 cases were obtained. In each case, the content of the separated individual Ti-oxide or Ti-oxyhydroxide phase corresponds to three folds the partially leached LPSR phase content. A careful investigation of the final products obtained from the 20 cases reflects the similarities between some of them. As only the associated individual molecular water content is different, only 10 alteration cases were considered. The chosen 10 cases are suspected to occur only where the unstable immobile titanium oxyhydroxide separated from the LPSR phase after the removal of the first definite iron content. In the chosen ten cases, the true ratio of Ti/(Ti+Fe), which corresponds only to the Ti and Fe contents in the actual remaining LPSR component phase, is 0.75, which is the same as the most stable lowest iron LPSR phase $\text{FeTi}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_3$. The false ratios that correspond to the total contents of Ti and Fe for all included phases contained within the alteration product for the remaining LPSR and the individual phases of Ti-oxide or Ti-oxyhydroxide are different, as their values range between 0.78 and 0.90.

Two cases of the chosen 10 are similar to the two suggested HPR formulas in [11]. Type II ilmenite alteration, in which ilmenite directly alters to HPR, was considered one of the mixed phases obtained from LPSR and the individual Ti-oxyhydroxide phase. This is an extended alteration process of the $\text{FeTi}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_3$ LPSR phase, due to iron leaching and hydrolysis processes followed by a separation process for the definite contents of Ti-oxyhydroxides to maintain the survived LPSR structure. When the separated Ti-bearing phase crystallizes in the triply twinned rutile phase structure, it appears to have the same XRD pattern of PSR or HPSR, in association with the survived remaining LPSR upon the hexagonal close-packed anion layers of the PSR structure. This justifies why the structure and the analyzed spot provide the XRD pattern of PSR or HPR. When the alteration rate of PSR is too fast, the successive gradual change will stop at any point between $\text{Fe}^{3+}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_9$ and $\text{Fe}^{3+}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_3$, or between $\text{Fe}^{3+}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_3$ and $\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{4.5}(\text{OH})_{4.5}$, or at slightly lower iron content, and the structure of PSR/LPSR will collapse. According to the crystallinity of the obtained products, micro- or crypto-individual Ti- and Fe- phases, the detected XRD patterns are governed.

In summary, ilmenite alteration is characterized by the oxidation of Fe^{2+} to Fe^{3+} followed by a continuous loss of Fe^{3+}

to form leached ilmenite and then PSR. This is a near-surface oxidizing process in a slightly acidic environment. The new approach presented in this study is that, on continuous iron leaching and approaching the LPSR phase $\text{FeTi}_3\text{O}_6(\text{OH})_3$, not only is iron separated, but also Ti-oxy-hydroxides are separated to form individual TiO_2 phases in association with the remaining LPSR phase. At a definite LPSR phase, the structure will break out into individual Ti- and Fe- bearing phases. Furthermore, in this study, the lower stability limit was lower than previously given [9, 28, 33], as it was around 0.5 mol% Fe or slightly lower, related to 3 mol% Ti. At any stage of the last alteration model, and according to changes in environmental conditions, especially acidity and water activity, the occurring LPSR phase can be completely broken out, giving leucoxene with Ti- and Fe- phases with or without identified crystallinity.

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REFERENCES

- [1] N. P. Subrahmanyam, N. K. Rao, D. Narasimhan, G. V. U. Rao, N. K. Jaggi, and K. R. P. M. Rao, "Alteration of Beach Sand Ilmenite from Manavalakurichi, Tamil Nadu, India," *Geological Society of India*, vol. 23, no. 4, pp. 168–174, Apr. 1982.
- [2] C. Palmer, "Arizonite, ferric metatitanate," *American Journal of Science*, vol. s4-28, no. 166, pp. 353–356, Oct. 1909, <https://doi.org/10.2475/ajs.s4-28.166.353>.
- [3] S. W. Bailey, R. J. Weege, E. N. Cameron, and H. R. Spedden, "The alteration of ilmenite in beach sands," *Economic Geology*, vol. 51, no. 3, pp. 263–279, May 1956, <https://doi.org/10.2113/gsecongeo.51.3.263>.
- [4] A. D. Bykov, "Proarizonite as a secondary mineral due to supergene alteration of ilmenite," in *Proceedings of the USSR Academy of Sciences*, 1964, vol. 156, no. 3, pp. 567–70.
- [5] A. K. Temple, "Alteration of ilmenite," *Economic Geology*, vol. 61, no. 4, pp. 695–714, Jun. 1966, <https://doi.org/10.2113/gsecongeo.61.4.695>.
- [6] J. W. Gruner, "The decomposition of ilmenite; discussion," *Economic Geology*, vol. 54, no. 7, pp. 1315–1316, Nov. 1959, <https://doi.org/10.2113/gsecongeo.54.7.1315>.
- [7] D. Carroll, "Ilmenite alteration under reducing conditions in unconsolidated sediments," *Economic Geology*, vol. 55, no. 3, pp. 618–619, May 1960, <https://doi.org/10.2113/gsecongeo.55.3.618>.
- [8] F. Dimanche and D. Bartholome, "The alteration of ilmenite in sediments," *Minerals Science Engineering*, vol. 8, pp. 187–201, 1976.
- [9] A. Mücke and J. N. Bhadra Chaudhuri, "The continuous alteration of ilmenite through pseudorutile to leucoxene," *Ore Geology Reviews*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 25–44, Feb. 1991, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-1368\(91\)90030-B](https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-1368(91)90030-B).
- [10] M. I. Pownceby, "Alteration and associated impurity element enrichment in detrital ilmenites from the Murray Basin, southeast Australia: a product of multistage alteration," *Australian Journal of Earth Sciences*, vol. 57, no. 2, pp. 243–258, Mar. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1080/08120090903521705>.
- [11] I. E. Grey and C. Li, "Hydroxylated pseudorutile derived from picroilmenite in the Murray Basin, southeastern Australia," *Mineralogical Magazine*, vol. 67, no. 4, pp. 733–747, Aug. 2003, <https://doi.org/10.1180/0026461036740130>.
- [12] C. C. Gonçalves and P. F. A. Braga, "Heavy Mineral Sands in Brazil: Deposits, Characteristics, and Extraction Potential of Selected Areas," *Minerals*, vol. 9, no. 3, Mar. 2019, Art. no. 176, <https://doi.org/10.3390/min9030176>.

- [13] A. Putnis and C. V. Putnis, "The mechanism of reequilibration of solids in the presence of a fluid phase," *Journal of Solid State Chemistry*, vol. 180, no. 5, pp. 1783–1786, May 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jssc.2007.03.023>.
- [14] R. Weibel and H. Friis, "Chapter 10 Alteration of Opaque Heavy Minerals as a Reflection of the Geochemical Conditions in Depositional and Diagenetic Environments," in *Developments in Sedimentology*, vol. 58, M. A. Mange and D. T. Wright, Eds. Elsevier, 2007, pp. 277–303.
- [15] M. Dieye, M. M. Thiam, A. Geneyton, and M. Gueye, "Monazite Recovery by Magnetic and Gravity Separation of Medium Grade Zircon Concentrate from Senegalese Heavy Mineral Sands Deposit," *Journal of Minerals and Materials Characterization and Engineering*, vol. 09, no. 06, pp. 590–608, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.4236/jmmce.2021.96038>.
- [16] M. I. Moustafa, "Mineralogy and beneficiation of some economic minerals in the Egyptian black sands," Ph.D. dissertation, Mansoura University, Dakahlia, Egypt, 2010.
- [17] N. Z. Boctor, "Mineralogical study of the opaque minerals in Rosetta-Damietta black sands," MSc Thesis, Cairo University, Cairo, Egypt, 1966.
- [18] M. A. Mikhail, "Distribution and sedimentation of ilmenite in black sands, west of Rosetta," Ph.D. dissertation, Cairo University, Cairo, Egypt, 1971.
- [19] N. M. Hammoud, "Concentration of monazite from Egyptian black sands, employing industrial techniques," MSc Thesis, Cairo University, Cairo, Egypt, 1966.
- [20] N. M. Hammoud, "Physical and chemical properties of some Egyptian beach economic minerals in relation to their concentration problems," Ph.D. dissertation, Cairo University, Cairo, Egypt, 1973.
- [21] A. A. M. Abdel-Karim, M. I. Moustafa, A. H. El-Afandy, and M. G. Barakat, "Mineralogy, Chemical Characteristics and Upgrading of Beach Ilmenite of the Top Meter of Black Sand Deposits of the Kafr Al-Sheikh Governorate, Northern Egypt," *Acta Geologica Sinica - English Edition*, vol. 91, no. 4, pp. 1326–1338, 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1111/1755-6724.13364>.
- [22] A. A. M. Abdel-Karim, S. M. Zaid, M. I. Moustafa, and M. G. Barakat, "Mineralogy, chemistry and radioactivity of the heavy minerals in the black sands, along the northern coast of Egypt," *Journal of African Earth Sciences*, vol. 123, pp. 10–20, Nov. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jafrearsci.2016.07.005>.
- [23] M. I. Moustafa, "Some Mineralogical Characteristics of the Egyptian Black Sand Beach Ilmenite Part I: Homogeneous Ilmenite and Titanhematite-Ferriilmenite Grains," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 9614–9631, Dec. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5296>.
- [24] M. I. Moustafa, "Some Mineralogical Characteristics of the Egyptian Black Sand Beach Ilmenite Part II: Rutile-Ilmenite and the Various Titanhematite Grains," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 9640–9653, Dec. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5297>.
- [25] M. I. Moustafa, "The Mineralogical and Chemical Composition of the Strongly Magnetic Egyptian Black Sand Altered Ilmenite," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 11298–11317, Aug. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.6025>.
- [26] M. I. Moustafa, "Study of the Mineralogical and Chemical Compositions of the Weakly Magnetic Fractions of the Egyptian Black Sand Altered Ilmenite," *Geosciences*, vol. 13, no. 6, Jun. 2023, Art. no. 170, <https://doi.org/10.3390/geosciences13060170>.
- [27] M. I. Moustafa, M. A. Tashkandi, and A. M. El-Sherif, "Detecting Mineral Resources and Suggesting a Physical Concentration Flowsheet for Economic Minerals at the Northern Border Region of Saudi Arabia," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 8617–8627, Jun. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4894>.
- [28] M. T. Frost, I. E. Grey, I. R. Harrowfield, and K. Mason, "The dependence of alumina and silica contents on the extent of alteration of weathered ilmenites from Western Australia," *Mineralogical Magazine*, vol. 47, no. 343, pp. 201–208, Jun. 1983, <https://doi.org/10.1180/minmag.1983.047.343.10>.
- [29] S. S. Ahmed, M. Y. Miah, C. Qumruzzaman, M. N. Zaman, A. B. Alam, and P. K. Biswas, "Alteration and Exsolution Characteristics of Ilmenites of Mohekhali Island, Chittagong, Bangladesh," *Bangladesh Journal of Scientific and Industrial Research*, vol. 45, no. 1, pp. 17–26, Jan. 1970, <https://doi.org/10.3329/bjsir.v45i1.5173>.
- [30] J. W. Gruner, "Hydrothermal oxidation and leaching experiments; their bearing on the origin of Lake Superior hematite-limonite ores," *Economic Geology*, vol. 25, no. 7, pp. 697–719, Nov. 1930, <https://doi.org/10.2113/gsecongeo.25.7.697>.
- [31] J. W. Gruner, "Hydrothermal oxidation and leaching experiments; their bearing on the origin of Lake Superior hematite-limonite ores; Part II," *Economic Geology*, vol. 25, no. 8, pp. 837–867, Dec. 1930, <https://doi.org/10.2113/gsecongeo.25.8.837>.
- [32] P. A. Schroeder, J. J. Le Golván, and M. F. Roden, "Weathering of ilmenite from granite and chlorite schist in the Georgia Piedmont," *American Mineralogist*, vol. 87, no. 11–12, pp. 1616–1625, Nov. 2002, <https://doi.org/10.2138/am-2002-11-1211>.
- [33] I. E. Grey and A. F. Reid, "The structure of pseudorutile and its role in the natural alteration of ilmenite," *American Mineralogist*, vol. 60, no. 9–10, pp. 898–906, Oct. 1975.
- [34] N. S. Hammoud, "Electrical separation in upgrading Egyptian beach zircon and rutile concentrates," presented at the XIIth International Mineral Processing Congress, Sao Paulo, Brazil, 1977, pp. 100–124.
- [35] M. G. Dyadchenko and A. Y. Khatuntseva, "Mineralogy and geochemistry of the weathering process in ilmenite," *Doklady Akademii Nauk SSR, Earth Sciences*, vol. 132, pp. 593–597, 1960.
- [36] E. F. Lener, "Mineral Chemistry of Heavy Minerals in the Old Hickory Deposit, Sussex and Dinwiddie Counties, Virginia," MSc Thesis, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University, Blacksburg, VA, USA, 1997.
- [37] V. Gevorkyan, "Some data on the initial stages of leucogenization of ilmenite from the sedimentary deposits of the northern Azov area," *Dopovidi Akademi Nauk Ukraini Koi RSR*, vol. 10, pp. 1366–1369, 1964.
- [38] G. Pe-Piper, D. J. W. Piper, and L. Dolansky, "Alteration of Ilmenite in the Cretaceous Sandstones of Nova Scotia, Southeastern Canada," *Clays and Clay Minerals*, vol. 53, no. 5, pp. 490–510, Oct. 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1346/CCMN.2005.0530506>.
- [39] S. Tetsopgang, J. Koyanagi, M. Enami, and K. Kihara, "Hydroxylated pseudorutile in an adamellite from the Nkambe area, Cameroon," *Mineralogical Magazine*, vol. 67, no. 3, pp. 509–516, Jun. 2003, <https://doi.org/10.1180/0026461036730113>.
- [40] A. Derkowski and A. Kuligiewicz, "Rehydroxylation in smectites and other clay minerals observed in-situ with a modified thermogravimetric system," *Applied Clay Science*, vol. 136, pp. 219–229, Feb. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clay.2016.11.030>.
- [41] V. A. Drits, A. Derkowski, and D. K. McCarty, "New insight into the structural transformation of partially dehydroxylated pyrophyllite," *American Mineralogist*, vol. 96, no. 1, pp. 153–171, Jan. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.2138/am.2011.3605>.
- [42] V. A. Drits, A. Derkowski, and D. K. McCarty, "Kinetics of partial dehydroxylation in dioctahedral 2:1 layer clay minerals," *American Mineralogist*, vol. 97, no. 5–6, pp. 930–950, May 2012, <https://doi.org/10.2138/am.2012.3971>.
- [43] V. D. Ignatiev, "Solid-phase mechanism of the ilmenite leucogenization," *Lithology and Mineral Resources*, vol. 34, pp. 184–189, 1999.
- [44] G. Teufer and A. K. Temple, "Pseudorutile—a New Mineral Intermediate between Ilmenite and Rutile in the N Alteration of Ilmenite," *Nature*, vol. 211, no. 5045, pp. 179–181, Jul. 1966, <https://doi.org/10.1038/211179b0>.

Analyzing the Effects of Lubrication Techniques on CNC Spindle Bearing Heat: An Experimental Investigation

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ABSTRACT

The machining ability and accuracy of a machine are determined by parameters such as the stiffness and load capacity of its spindle unit. In addition, the effectiveness and technique of lubrication and cooling can significantly affect the operational characteristics of the machine spindle. The current study investigated the effects of two different lubrication methods, grease and air-oil mixture, on the temperature which is generated at the spindle bearings of a Computer Numerical Control (CNC) machine. The temperature distribution and rise rate of the bearings were measured using a thermal imaging camera and thermocouples. The results indicated that the air-oil mixture method was more effective in dissipating heat and reducing the temperature of the bearings than the grease method, due to the direct cooling provided by the air-oil mixture to the bearing balls, resulting in improved lubrication efficiency and heat exchange with the environment. Compared to the grease lubrication method, the temperature of the bearings was lower by 7°C to 9°C depending on the position of the bearing on the CNC spindle. Therefore, it is recommended to use the air-oil mixture lubrication method, especially for high-speed processing on CNC machines. However, the discharge of oil particles from the ventilation system should be carefully controlled. Overall, the findings offer valuable insights into optimizing lubrication methods for CNC machines to enhance processing quality and reduce the impact of temperature on the bearing performance.

Keywords-spindle bearing; lubrication method; temperature distribution

I. INTRODUCTION

The demand for high-speed machining has risen in modern manufacturing as it enables the production of complex and advanced products [1]. However, the high spindle rotation speed generates more heat, which can lead to stiffness and deformation issues. To address this problem, several cooling and lubrication methods have been proposed, such as air-oil cooling, to improve lubrication and cooling efficiency. The stiffness of the spindle unit is a crucial factor affecting the machining quality of machine tools [2, 3]. High-speed machining is necessary in order to produce more complex products. However, it generates heat and reduces the stiffness or increases deformation of the spindle [4-7]. Various methods have been proposed to enhance the efficiency of lubrication and cooling systems, and among them, grease and air-oil mixture lubrication have been studied using numerical simulations [8]. On the other hand, a study conducted in 2021 indicated a similarity in the trend of temperature variation over

working time between experimental and numerical simulation studies when lubricated with grease in all bearings of the CNC spindle unit [9]. Various lubrication methods have been developed to minimize heat generation at bearings, including grease, oil splash, and oil mist. Among these methods, liquid droplets have been identified as a promising option for enhancing lubrication and cooling, due to their effective convection and heat transfer properties [10]. A mixture of oil-air is a more effective lubrication and cooling method that saves lubricant and is preferred in modern machining industry [11, 12]. Authors in [13] investigated the effect of heat on machining accuracy, simulated the heat transfer process and analyzed thermal coupling using finite element analysis [13]. The cooling capacity of the spindle cooling system was also simulated, and the parameters provide a reference value for actual model building. Authors in [14] conducted a study investigating the performance of high-speed spindles using oil/air lubrication, with a focus on the effects of various lubrication parameters and preloads on temperature increase,

thermal deformation, and static stiffness. The study applied the Taguchi method to determine optimal lubrication conditions that minimize temperature increase and provide a useful tool for designing high-speed spindles with sufficient static stiffness [14]. Authors in [15] investigated the film-forming behavior under oil-air lubrication and oil-jet lubrication. Their results showed that oil-air lubrication has a higher oil supply efficiency and slower reduction in film thickness in starved regime, due to the contribution of micron-order oil droplets that improve oil supply efficiency [15]. Additionally, lubricating oil can be supplemented with additives to enhance lubrication efficiency, reducing friction and component wear within the machine [16].

Spindle bearings are essential components in machine tools, and their performance can significantly impact the overall productivity and quality of the machining process. Proper lubrication is critical to ensure the smooth operation and extended life of these bearings. In recent years, various lubrication methods have been proposed and investigated regarding CNC spindle bearings, including oil, grease, and air-oil mixtures. However, the choice of lubrication method and the appropriate lubricant type can significantly impact the thermal and dynamic behavior of the spindle, affecting its load-carrying capacity, accuracy, and stability. Therefore, it is important to investigate the effects of different lubrication methods on CNC spindle bearing performance to optimize the machining process and improve overall efficiency. Although these methods efficiently lubricate and cool the bearings, they still face problems of inaccurate monitoring and control of ball bearings, which need further improvement. A lubrication system was developed for the bearings of the spindle unit of a high-speed milling machine to investigate and regulate the heat generation and transfer process during high-speed operation. The system combines the mechanical components with control, measurement, and monitoring features for the lubrication mode of the bearings of spindle unit. The integration of the mechanical system, control system, measurement system, and lubrication mode monitoring system is a key feature of this system. The functional requirements of the system were designed, including simulating the spindle unit's operation, ensuring sufficient stiffness, integrated space for lubrication, cooling, control, measurement, and monitoring systems, and providing sufficient lubricant to keep the bearing running smoothly, ensuring optimum temperature. The control, measurement, and monitoring system generate data for analysis by controlling the system. In order to identify the integration requirements, it is crucial to understand the heat generation and transfer mechanism within the spindle unit. This knowledge serves as the foundation for selecting specific and accurate system parameters.

In this study, the temperature of the spindle bearings in the CNC machine will be monitored using a sensor system and will be collected for processing to evaluate the quality of lubrication methods suitable for the working conditions of the spindle bearing unit. Two lubrication methods, grease and air-oil mixture, were performed at a spindle speed of approximately 7000 rpm for 1 h. The experiments were conducted under the same working conditions.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The spindle unit generates heat which is transferred from the bearings to the housing. While using air-oil-cooled lubrication, a portion of the heat is absorbed by the air stream. However, with grease lubrication, some of the heat is transferred to the lubricant and then to the housing, which is eventually dissipated into the environment. Therefore, it is crucial to estimate the amount of heat produced within the spindle and the heat transferred through the bearings before constructing an experimental system for measuring the temperature of the spindle unit. To examine the effectiveness of the spindle unit's lubrication system, two lubrication techniques were utilized: (1) a water-cooled and grease-lubricated system, and (2) a high-pressure air-oil mixture system. The air-oil mixture will be generated by pumping oil from the tank into the mixer, where compressed air pressure will break it into small particles, creating a high-pressure oil force that can easily penetrate high-temperature areas. For the experiments, a CNC machine was integrated with a spindle ER16-80SK 24k that has a power capacity of 1.5 kW as depicted in Figure 1. The spindle is equipped with bearing of 7002 type and is driven by a three-phase asynchronous motor controlled by an inverter. The system monitors the spindle speed, current, voltage, torque, and alarm signals. Temperature sensors are attached to the bearings to collect real-time temperature data, which are saved in a computer for further analysis. A detailed schematic of the experimental air-oil cooling and lubrication system, including its components, is presented in Figure 2.

Fig. 1. Cross-section of the spindle unit.

Fig. 2. A diagram illustrating the principle of the proposed air-oil cooling and lubrication system.

When analyzing a ball bearing, the parameters to be considered include ball diameter (d), rotational speed (V), and rotation diameter (D). The ball rotates at a velocity ω_b and the primary causes of heat generation in the bearing are the load torque and the ball torque [17]. The total heat generated can be estimated by:

$$H_f = \omega_b M_s \quad (1)$$

The angular velocity of the ball is denoted by ω_b . The torque generated in the bearing, which includes the torque caused by slip and the gyroscope of the ball, is denoted by M_s and is expressed as follows:

$$M_s = (M_{ds} + M_{gr})K \quad (2)$$

The coefficient K varies depending on the accuracy class of the spindle unit. The torque due to sliding can be expressed as:

$$M_{ds} = \frac{PD_0 z}{4d_b} \left(1 - \frac{d_b^2}{D_0^2} \cos^2 \alpha \right) (r_0 B_0 - r_i B_i) f \quad (3)$$

The coefficient $B_0 = B_i = 1$ is determined by the geometry of the inner and outer rim of the bearing, while r_0 and r_i refer to the deformation of the inner and outer rim surfaces and α represents the contact angle, with f being the friction coefficient. The gyroscope torque of the ball is estimated by:

$$M_{gr} = \frac{\pi}{60} d_b^2 \frac{\gamma}{g} \omega_b z \sin \alpha \quad (4)$$

Fig. 3. Experimental system for spindle unit integration: (1) Air-oil supply, (2) air-oil vent hole, (3) temperature sensors.

Temperature sensors (Figure 3) are utilized to continuously monitor the spindle bearing's lubrication status, observe the temperature of the bearings, and record the spindle's consumption current value. The sensors are placed on the outer rings of the spindle unit while the consumption current is measured by an inverter and transmitted to the controller. The design parameters are used to set the working conditions with

an assumption of ambient temperature at 25°C and assuming environment air pressure of 1 bar. The following section presents the experimental results for the temperature generated in the spindle bearings, and Table I lists the experimental parameters using the air-oil mixture lubrication method.

TABLE I. EXPERIMENTAL PARAMETERS OF THE AIR-OIL MIXTURE LUBRICATION

Air pressure	7.5 bar
Air flow rate	1200 l/hr
Oil flow rate	180 mm ³ /hr
Oil type	Tona 68
Spindle speed	7000 rpm
Applied load on shaft	16 N
Observation time	3600 s

When using the air-oil lubrication method, the spindle unit of the machine tool is lubricated and cooled continuously during the operation. The lubrication status is monitored and maintained to ensure optimal performance. The system closely monitors parameters such as bearing temperature, oil level, air pressure, and spindle consumption current to assess the lubrication status of the spindle bearings. To optimize the lubrication and cooling process, the air pressure should be maintained at 7.5 bar to ensure proper shredding of the oil flow. An inverter is used to measure the spindle's consumption current, and the obtained data is transmitted to the controller to avoid system errors if the designed amount of lubricating oil is not supplied. If the bearing temperature rises, and the consumption current reaches a preset value while all other requirements are met, the system will shut down and an alarm will be triggered. The controller will allow the oil pump and air valve to operate only when all criteria are met.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To evaluate the temperature generated in the bearings of the spindle unit in the CNC milling machine using two different lubrication methods, i.e. grease and air-oil mixture, the experimental environment was maintained at constant working parameters. The spindle was set to rotate at a constant speed of 7000 rpm, and temperature readings were taken over a 1 hr period using temperature sensors located at the bearing locations. A numerical simulation study on lubrication using air-oil mixture and grease has been conducted, which shows that at the speed of 7000 rpm, the temperature at the main spindle unit is the lowest. On the other hand, the temperature at the roller bearing position increases sharply during the time interval from 0 to 2000 s and reaches a stable value after about 2250 s.

From the results shown in Figure 4(a), it can be observed that at the rotational speed of 7000 rpm, the temperature characteristic curves of the bearings have similarities to the numerical simulation results mentioned above. Bearings 3 and 4 have higher temperatures than bearing 1 due to the limitations in heat dissipation space. The temperature characteristic curves of the external area of the 3 bearings increase rapidly during the first 1000 s, then gradually increase. The temperature stabilizes after 3400 s, and the bearings gradually reach a state of thermal saturation that persists until the end of the experiment. It can be stated that the temperature increases after

a certain period of operation, which reduces the viscosity of the grease, decreases the friction between the layers of lubricants in the bearings, leading to a decrease in the rate of temperature rise, and reaching a stable state.

Fig. 4. The temperature at the bearings was measured during 3600 s of spindle operation at 7000 rpm using two different lubrication methods: (a) grease and (b) air-oil mixture.

The air-oil cooling lubrication method shows similar characteristics in the characteristic curve when compared to the grease lubrication method. However, the temperature rise rate is slower, indicating the effectiveness of the air-oil lubrication method. The air-oil mixture is easily able to fill the clearance between the relatively moving surfaces, and the high-pressure air-oil flow with continuous movement leading to better heat dissipation. Moreover, it is apparent that at bearing 1, direct cooling lubrication by air-oil mixture causes a significant decrease in temperature and slower temperature rise, with a maximum temperature difference of 7°C (about 14.5%) recorded compared to the grease lubrication method (as depicted in Figure 4(b)). When comparing the two lubrication methods, the maximum temperature difference values for rolling bearings 3 and 4 are about 7°C (about 11.5%) and 9°C (about 15%), respectively. However, these values were concentrated in the temperature range approaching stability, which is very significant in cases of long-term processing. The lubrication efficiency using an air-oil mixture will be better and contribute to reducing the influence of temperature on processing quality on the CNC machine.

Fig. 5. Comparison of the temperature at the bearings for 2 lubrication methods during 1 hr of operation at 7000 rpm.

Figure 5 illustrates the temperature difference over time between the two lubrication methods. The temperature at the rolling elements is lower when lubricated with air-oil mixture than with grease. This can be explained by the higher viscosity of grease (15 mm²/s) compared to oil (68 mm²/s). Grease forms a thick layer around the ball, hindering its movement and increasing the friction between the moving surfaces. Furthermore, it takes time for the grease to reach the friction areas between the ball and the inner and outer races, resulting in slower lubrication efficiency than air-oil mixture. Moreover, the lubrication efficiency of grease decreases over time, significantly affecting the bearing performance. Therefore, when operating at higher speeds, using grease lubrication is not recommended due to its limitations.

Regarding the cooling performance, grease lubrication combined with water as a cooling agent is continuously pumped during operation. However, when the spindle operates for a long time, the temperature of the water increases, reducing the cooling efficiency. This issue largely depends on the optimization of the cooling pump system. Nevertheless, water only cools the outer race directly, while the main heat source is the inner ball, limiting the cooling capacity significantly.

On the other hand, the method of lubrication using an air-oil mixture overcomes most of the drawbacks of lubrication with grease. Enough lubricating oil with high pressure is directly supplied to the bearing, permeating and deeply penetrating the friction areas. Additionally, the oil is continuously supplied to prevent the degradation of the lubricant after prolonged use. With the help of compressed air pressure, the lubricating oil is directly transported to the primary thermal area of the rolling bearing, providing direct cooling to the bearing balls, resulting in better lubrication efficiency than the grease lubrication method combined with indirect water cooling. Indeed, the compressed air pressure will break down the oil particles into very small ones, making them able to easily penetrate frictional areas and improve the lubrication efficiency. This pressure also helps enhance the efficiency of the heat exchange process with the environment. Therefore, it can be said that the lubrication method using an air-oil mixture is encouraged to apply, especially in high-speed processing cases on CNC machines. However, it also shows

certain limitations on the surrounding environment due to oil particles being discharged after lubrication. This requires attention to the operation of the ventilation system during processing.

The investigation on the impact of specific input parameters, such as the pressure and flow rate of the gas-oil mixture, on the lubrication quality of the spindle bearing unit is currently underway and will be presented in upcoming studies.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the current experimental study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of two lubrication methods, i.e. grease and air-oil mixture, on the temperature generated at the bearings of a CNC milling machine spindle unit. The results showed that the air-oil cooling lubrication method was more effective in dissipating heat, resulting in a slower temperature rise rate and a lower temperature at the rolling elements compared to the grease lubrication method. Moreover, the air-oil mixture provided direct cooling to the bearing balls, leading to better lubrication efficiency and heat exchange with the environment. Accordingly, the temperature of the bearings decreases from 7°C to 9°C depending on the position of the bearing on the CNC spindle compared to the grease lubrication method. Therefore, the lubrication method using an air-oil mixture is encouraged, especially in high-speed processing cases on CNC machines.

However, attention must be paid to the operation of the ventilation system during processing to mitigate the discharge of oil particles. Overall, the current study provides valuable insight into the optimization of lubrication methods for CNC machines in order to improve the processing quality and reduce the influence of temperature on the performance of the bearings.

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REFERENCES

- [1] X. J. Xuan, Z. H. Haung, K. D. Wu, and J. P. Hung, "Prediction of the Frequency Response Function of a Tool Holder-Tool Assembly Based on Receptance Coupling Method," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 3556–3560, Dec. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2372>.
- [2] V.-H. Pham, M.-T. Nguyen, and T.-A. Bui, "Oil pressure and viscosity influence on stiffness of the hydrostatic spindle bearing of a medium-sized circular grinding machine," *International Journal of Modern Physics B*, vol. 34, no. 22n24, Sep. 2020, Art. no. 2040156, <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0217979220401566>.
- [3] N. B. Serradj, A. D. K. Ali, and M. E. A. Ghernaout, "A Contribution to the Thermal Field Evaluation at the Tool-Part Interface for the Optimization of Machining Conditions," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 7750–7756, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4235>.
- [4] A. Zivkovic, M. Knezev, M. Zeljkovic, S. Navalusic, and L. D. Beju, "A study of thermo-elastic characteristics of the machine tool spindle," in *9th International Conference on Manufacturing Science and Education – MSE 2019 "Trends in New Industrial Revolution,"* 2019, vol. 290, Art. no. 01009, <https://doi.org/10.1051/mateconf/201929001009>.
- [5] L. Yu, Z. Xing, M. Gao, and L. Shang, "Research on the influence of spindle temperature rise of drilling and tapping machine on machining accuracy," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 1885, no. 2, Dec. 2021, Art. no. 022002, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1885/2/022002>.
- [6] T. H. Le, V. B. Pham, and T. D. Hoang, "Surface Finish Comparison of Dry and Coolant Fluid High-Speed Milling of JIS SDK61 Mould Steel," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 8023–8028, Feb. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4594>.
- [7] A. D. K. Ali, N. B. Serradj, and M. E. A. Ghernaout, "Cutting Parameter Optimization based on Online Temperature Measurements," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 9861–9866, Feb. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5348>.
- [8] T.-A. Bui and Q.-T. Vu, "A Study on an Oil-Air Mixed Lubrication Monitoring System for Spindle Unit of CNC Milling Machine," in *Proceedings of the 2nd Annual International Conference on Material, Machines and Methods for Sustainable Development (MMMS2020)*, 2021, pp. 920–928, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-69610-8_122.
- [9] D.-D. Le, Q.-T. Vu, and T.-A. Bui, "Simulation and Experimental Study of Heat in Grease-Lubricated CNC Milling Machine Spindle Bearings," in *Proceedings of the International Conference on Advanced Mechanical Engineering, Automation, and Sustainable Development 2021 (AMAS2021)*, 2022, pp. 462–467, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-99666-6_67.
- [10] M. Handawi, A. E. I. Elshwain, M. Y. Noordin, N. Redzuan, and D. Kurniawan, "Comparison between Nitrogen-Oil-Mist and Air-Oil-Mist Condition when Turning of Hardened Tool Stainless Steel," *Applied Mechanics and Materials*, vol. 660, pp. 18–22, 2014, <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMM.660.18>.
- [11] O. Maeda, Y. Cao, and Y. Altintas, "Expert spindle design system," *International Journal of Machine Tools and Manufacture*, vol. 45, no. 4, pp. 537–548, Apr. 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmachtools.2004.08.021>.
- [12] S. Li and Y. Wu, "A Study on Oil/Air Lubrication and Preload of a High Frequency Fully Ceramic Motor Spindle," in *2010 International Conference on E-Product E-Service and E-Entertainment*, Henan, China, Aug. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICEEE.2010.5661555>.
- [13] C. Zhao and X. Guan, "Thermal Analysis and Experimental Study on the Spindle of the High-Speed Machining Center," *AASRI Procedia*, vol. 1, pp. 207–212, Jan. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aasri.2012.06.032>.
- [14] C.-H. Wu and Y.-T. Kung, "A parametric study on oil/air lubrication of a high-speed spindle," *Precision Engineering*, vol. 29, no. 2, pp. 162–167, Apr. 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.precisioneng.2004.06.005>.
- [15] H. Liang, D. Guo, L. Ma, and J. Luo, "The film forming behavior at high speeds under oil–air lubrication," *Tribology International*, vol. 91, pp. 6–13, Nov. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.triboint.2015.06.010>.
- [16] T.-A. Bui, V.-H. Pham, D.-T. Nguyen, and N.-T. Bui, "Effectiveness of Lubricants and Fly Ash Additive on Surface Damage Resistance under ASTM Standard Operating Conditions," *Coatings*, vol. 13, no. 5, May 2023, Art. no. 851, <https://doi.org/10.3390/coatings13050851>.
- [17] T. A. Stolarski, Ed., *Tribology in Machine Design*. Elsevier, 1999.

Reinforced Concrete Columns Insulated by Different Gypsum Layers Exposed to 900°C One Side Fire Flame

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effect of high-temperature fire flame on reinforced concrete columns coated with a layer of gypsum insulation. Six samples were cast and cured in a hot water bath at 67°C, covered on one side by 10 and 20 mm thick layers of gypsum plaster. The samples were exposed to a 900°C fire flame in a hydrocarbon fire furnace for one and two hours. The results showed that the gypsum plaster layer prevented a high-temperature rise within the core of the column. The differences between all gypsum-coated columns varied compared to those of the reference samples. The gypsum-coated columns had reduced axial displacements and no spalling and visible cracks on their faces. The improvement in the compressive strength of concrete will be discussed in a future paper. This study was carried out following ACI-318 and ASTM C1529.

Keywords-hydrocarbon fire; one face; temperature evolution; ASTM 1529

I. INTRODUCTION

Experimental research on gypsum plasterboards involves setting them ablaze with simulated fire. In [1], a large-scale fire test was conducted on steel stud gypsum plasterboards to evaluate their fire resistance. The results showed that mechanical stress had little impact on the thermal behavior of gypsum plasterboards. An increase in cracks was induced by applying both temperature and load whereas the features of the material that were temperature-dependent could be detected. The thermal properties of the materials change as a result of the heating and cooling processes. In [2], a multi-phase approach was followed to predict heat transfer within the gypsum layer under fire exposure, including conduction, mass transfer, and condensation/evaporation, and considering water vapor transport and condensation in the porous structure. The calculated temperatures above 100°C were adequate up to 2 cm from the fireside and a numerical model was proposed to calculate the temperatures in the gypsum blocks for longer distances. Experimental investigations of gypsum plasterboards were performed under exposure to natural fire, and thermal properties were determined for both the heating and cooling phases. The results of a large-scale fire test on loaded steel beams were extracted, and the fire protection behavior was tested under a standard fire curve, both with and without mechanical load.

In [3], the thermal behavior of gypsum plasterboards for steel elements was investigated by exposure to natural fire. The results showed a clear dependence on the heating and cooling rate, while the thermal material properties changed within the heating and cooling phase. In [4], a simple two-dimensional model was validated to predict heat transfer through gypsum-board/wood-stud walls exposed to fire. In [5], the influence of depth and distance between studs on the fire resistance of Lightweight Timber-Framed (LTF) walls lined with gypsum plasterboards was investigated, using numerical simulations and experimental tests. In [6], the fire protection performance of gypsum board assemblies was investigated, presenting a hybrid numerical-experimental method to extract the thermal conductivity of various gypsum products at elevated temperatures, performing high-temperature mechanical tests and developing a 2D finite element model to simulate the structural performance of gypsum boards in a fire. In [7], the high-temperature exposure of normal concrete covered with gypsum plaster layers was studied. The experimental results showed that concrete with gypsum layers at 400 and 700°C had less losses in compressive strength, modulus of rupture, and modulus of elasticity. In [8], the results of exposure to 400 and 700°C of normal concrete covered with gypsum and plaster layers were presented, showing that their ultimate load capacity and load-deflection curves were better than the uncoated reference samples.

This study investigated the effect of high-temperature fire flame on reinforced concrete columns coated with 10 and 20 mm thick gypsum insulation layers. Six samples were cast and cured in a hot water bath at 67°C, covered on one side by 10 and 20 mm thick layers of gypsum plaster, and then exposed to a 900°C fire flame in a hydrocarbon fire furnace. Three samples, without coating (R), with a 10 mm gypsum coating (1G), and with a 20 mm gypsum coating (2G), were exposed to fire for 1 hr, and 3 respective samples were exposed for 2 hr.

II. THE EXPERIMENT

The tests on the square reinforced concrete columns were conducted at the site of Reyah Al-Moasem, a concrete provider company. The experimental procedure consisted of 6 fire tests supporting both ends of the column. Two columns were used as reference samples without having a protective cover, two columns were covered with 10mm gypsum, and the last two columns were covered with 20mm gypsum. All columns were subjected to the same fire and time conditions, at 900° C for one or two hours. The tests simulated an actual fire scenario in a building to observe the effect of a gypsum layer on the reinforced concrete column by one face of fire exposure.

III. TEST SET-UP

A. Characteristics of the Specimens

The test specimens were reinforced concrete columns having 1500 mm height and 150×150 mm cross-sections. Concrete had a compressive strength of 28 MPa and the steel reinforcement bar had a yield of 418 MPa. After 24 hr of accelerated curing at 67°C, the specimens were ready to test. All specimens were similar in dimensions, steel reinforcement, curing time, concrete compressive strength, and number of stirrups. Gypsum layers of 10 and 20 mm thickness were attached to the respective specimens. A 1750×1250×750 mm water tank was used, connected to a thermometer and having three 3000 W electric heaters. The water was heated to 67°C with a curing duration of approximately 24 hr to reach maximum strength [9]. All specimens were prepared with reinforcement bars and stirrups of 12 and 6 mm diameter and assembled as a frame according to ACI-318 [10]. To strengthen the column, a 50×50×3 mm square steel plate was fixed at both ends, rounding the ends. Preparation of the specimen started with connecting the main reinforcement bars and stirrups. The reinforcement bars were then carefully placed inside the mold to achieve the desired concrete cover. All specimens were instrumented with Type-K thermocouples, placed in three sections along their vertical direction, each containing 5-6 thermocouples, as shown in Figure 1. Then, the steel hooks and longitudinal reinforcement bars were connected to the stirrups by wires. After these steel works and the concrete casting, the specimens were left to cure in the hot water tank.

B. Mechanical Properties

Coarse aggregate sized 4-19, C28 compressive concrete, and reinforcing steel bars of 418 MPa yield were used for all test specimens. The concrete cover related to the stirrups for all tested columns was 20 mm on each side.

Fig. 1. Thermocouple's location through column sample cross-section.

C. Specimens Preparation

The specimens were placed in the furnace horizontally. The longitudinal steel reinforcement bars were traditionally framed according to ACI-318 [10]. The main steel reinforcement area bars were selected to have the same ratio values per cross-section for all specimens tested. All specimens were cast identically and all the column specimens were exposed to furnace fire flame. The inside dimensions of the furnace were 500×650×1250 mm. The furnace could be opened from both ends, and the heating was provided by propane gas designed to cover all the perimeter exposed to direct fire flame. Figure 2 shows the design of the furnace. Each top and bottom side contained 10 gas jets. The furnace sides had 5 jets each. Each jet group for all sides was connected to the master gas hose in a separate way to make it more easily used and controlled by a gas valve regulator. The furnace was covered by 200×100×50 mm thermal insulation bricks and had holes to allow the flame to pass through the propane gas tube to the interior of the furnace perimeter.

D. Test Installation

Figures 2 and 3 show a broad view of the experimental devices. The furnace was constructed using cast steel and insulating blocks to maintain the required temperature for the duration of the test. According to ACI-318 [10], the specimen was placed horizontally inside the furnace. The fire was directed at the upper face and right side to give the entire column specimen the highest amount of exposure to fire. The sections were 375, 750, and 1125 mm from the base of the column, respectively, and the thermocouples were positioned within the column specimen at three levels in the cross-section. The furnace was capable of reaching temperatures of 1300°C and applying fire curves with various heating rates. This study used the ASTM 1529 standard fire curve [11].

Fig. 2. Top view of the furnace system.

Fig. 3. Front view for furnace system cross-section.

Type-K thermocouples, installed at 5 different levels through the cross-sections of the tested columns, were used to measure the temperatures of the specimens. Six thermocouples were evenly distributed throughout each cross-section, one attached to the longitudinal and transverse reinforcement bars and the others embedded in the concrete at varying depths: the first one close to the surface, the second near the center, the third in the middle between them, and the fourth one close to the stirrups at the top level. Four shielded type-K thermocouples were used to monitor the temperatures within the furnace during the tests. A 24-channel temperature-capable data logger was used to collect the data. The two ends of the

column specimens were connected by two steel bars that were welded to them, and the other two sides were fastened with a steel plate with holes cut for one steel bar to allow the other to move freely [12-14]. The second dial gauge was positioned using the same process on the bottom side. One thermocouple was positioned between the gypsum layer and the column's face to record the temperature passage to the column's concrete face. All dial gauges were placed outside the furnace for maximum heat protection.

E. Test Method

This study aimed to investigate how the gypsum layer influences a structural member's capacity to survive fire by exposing concrete column specimens to flames that imitate actual fire accident conditions. This test aimed to achieve 900°C and document the differences in temperature between all specimens, describing temperature-related deformation. Thermal elongation occurred while the test specimens were exposed to the fire and were manually captured by a camera with a time stamp for the test application. The temperature was recorded between the four insulated thermocouples placed on four sides of the specimens. The specimens were exposed for one and two hours at temperatures of 900°C, with the gypsum coating on one face of the column being 10mm and 20mm thick, respectively. The specimens were heated to their maximum fire exposure and brought to the desired temperature in 8 to 12 minutes [11].

Fig. 4. Test installation and samples.

IV. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

A. Temperature Evolution

Concrete elements are affected to different degrees by the heat generated by fire for a certain period. Figures 5-8 show that the temperature begins to rise linearly for all specimens covered with a gypsum layer, while the temperature rise is steady and non-linear in uncoated specimens. Table I shows the temperature values recorded by the thermocouples T1, T2, T3, T4, and T5 and their variation over time. The temperature

increases by more than twice in the core of the uncoated specimens through the surface area. This increase is slower for specimens covered with a gypsum protection layer during the burning period of 1 hr. Increasing the fire exposure period leads to higher temperatures. For the uncoated reference specimens, this increase reached its peak in the area near the surface (T5), unlike the specimens protected by the gypsum layer, where the temperature rise was gradual and almost constant and did not exceed 313°C when exposed to a flame temperature exceeding 900°C for a burning period of two continuous hours.

Fig. 5. Time-temperature comparison for R and 2G in cross-sections.

Fig. 7. Time-temperature comparison for R and 2G in cross-sections.

Fig. 6. Time-temperature comparison for R and 1G in cross-sections.

Fig. 8. Time-temperature comparison for R and 1G in cross-sections.

TABLE I. TEMPERATURE VALUES THROUGH THERMOCOUPLES

Column reference	Gypsum layer thickness (mm)	Fire exposure duration (min)	Range of exposure (min)	T1 (°C)	T2 (°C)	T3 (°C)	T4 (°C)	T5 (°C)	T-surface (°C)	T-rebar (°C)
Sq-R-900-1F-1h-L	0	60	R30	88.5	106.5	157.5	178.5	231	900	146
			R60	186	190.5	325.5	439.5	642	900	231
Sq-1G-900-1F-1h-L	10	60	R30	58	65	75	96	101	275	65
			R60	95	111	119	154	176	442	112
Sq-2G-900-1F-1h-L	20	60	R30	75	82	83	89	93	210	83
			R60	115	115	117	126	132	342	109
Sq-R-900-1F-2h-L	0	120	R30	114	139	140	284	505	900	150
			R60	149	246	249	443	685	900	238
			R90	209	336	340	512	756	900	315
			R120	280	413	417	591	800	900	382
Sq-1G-900-1F-2h-L	10	120	R30	74	78	84	105	107	202	65
			R60	110	111	116	164.5	184	311	112
			R90	130	131	149	222	240	386	155
			R120	149	166	198	281	313	451	218
Sq-2G-900-1F-2h-L	20	120	R30	55	69	74	78	100	141	83
			R60	67	87	96	104	125	271	119
			R90	77	107	118	132	170	327	146
			R120	84	127	143	161	235	373	176

TABLE II. TEMPERATURE REDUCTION RATIO

Column reference	Range of Exposure (min)	Reduction ratio %						
		T1 %	T2 %	T3 %	T4 %	T5 %	T-surface %	T-rebar %
Sq-1G-900-1F-1h-L	R30	34.46	38.96	52.38	46.21	56.27	69.44	55.47
	R60	48.92	41.73	63.44	64.96	72.58	53.11	51.51
Sq-2G-900-1F-1h-L	R30	15.25	23.0	47.3	50.14	59.74	76.55	43.15
	R60	38.17	39.63	64.0	71.33	79.43	62.00	52.81
Sq-1G-900-1F-2h-L	R30	35	43.88	40.0	57.66	78.81	77.55	65.66
	R60	26.17	54.87	53.41	62.86	73.13	65.44	52.94
	R90	37.79	61.0	56.17	56.64	68.25	57.11	50.79
	R120	46.78	59.8	52.51	52.45	60.87	49.88	42.93
Sq-2G-900-1F-2h-L	R30	51.75	50.35	47.14	68.54	80.19	84.33	38.0
	R60	55.0	64.63	61.44	76.52	81.75	69.88	50.0
	R90	63.15	68.15	65.29	74.21	77.51	63.66	53.65
	R120	70.0	69.24	65.7	72.75	70.62	58.55	53.92

B. Thermal Reduction Comparison

The reference columns (R) experienced high-temperature values compared with the specimens covered by 10 (1G) and 20 mm (2G) gypsum plaster cover, noted as 1G and 2G, respectively. Table II shows the temperature reduction ratios for all thermocouple recordings. The differences between Sq-R-900-1F-1h-L and Sq-1G-900-1F-1h-L show that the reduction in temperature values was about 34.46%, 38.96%, 52.38%, 46.21%, and 56.27% for thermocouples T1, T2, T3, T4, and T5, respectively, for 30 min of fire exposure. For the same specimens and thermocouples, the reduction ratios were 48.92%, 41.73%, 63.44%, 64.96%, and 72.58% after 60 min of fire exposure. For the specimens Sq-R-900-1F-1h-L and Sq-2G-900-1F-1h-L, the temperature reduction was 15.25%, 23%, 47.3%, 50.14%, and 59.74% for 30 min of exposure and 38.17%, 39.63%, 64%, 71.33%, and 79.43%, respectively, for 60 min. The comparison between specimens Sq-R-900-1F-2h-L and Sq-1G-900-1F-2h-L showed temperature reductions of 35%, 43.88%, and 40.0%, 57.66%, and 78.81%, for 30 min, 26.17%, 54.87%, 53.41%, 62.86%, and 73.13%, and 37.79%, for 60 min, 61.0%, 56.17%, 56.64%, and 68.25%, and 46.78%, for 90 min, and 59.8%, 52.51%, 52.45%, and 60.87% for 120 min of exposure. The specimens Sq-R-900-1F-2h-L and Sq-2G-900-1F-2h-L showed respective reductions of 51.7%, 50.35%, 47.1%, 68.54%, and 80.19% for 30 min, 55.0%, 64.63%, 61.44%, 76.52%, and 81.75% for 60 min, 63.15%, 68.15%, 65.29%, 74.21%, and 77.51% for 90 min, and 70.0%, 69.24%, 65.7%, 72.75%, and 70.62% for 120 min of exposure.

A thermocouple was placed between the gypsum plaster cover and the face of the concrete to study the direct fire exposure reduction between the reference and the covered specimens. The gypsum plaster cover indicated a large compartment of heat transfer between the specimens. The difference in temperature for Sq-R-900-1F-1h-L and Sq-1G-900-1F-1h-L was 69.44% and 53.11% for 30 and 60 min of fire exposure, respectively. For Sq-R-900-1F-1h-L and Sq-2G-900-1F-1h-L the difference was 76.55% and 62.00% for 30 and 60 min, respectively. The temperature reduction ratios between Sq-R-900-1F-2h-L and Sq-2G-900-1F-2h-L were 84.33%, 69.88%, 63.66%, and 58.55%, for 30, 60, 90, and 120 min of fire exposure. These results show that the temperature reduction varied for all covered column specimens, indicating that the most useful gypsum protection layer was in Sq-2G-900-1F-2h-L, which showed maximum protection.

The temperature in the cross-section center (T1) throughout the gypsum layer was reduced by 58.55% to the rest of the column fibers, showing that they resisted the fire effect on both concrete and rebars efficiently. For 60 min of fire exposure, the temperature reduction values were convergent and efficient in protecting the specimen. The gypsum protection layer efficiently affected the rebar temperature conductivity, as the temperature was lower by 55.47% and 51.51% for 30 and 60 min exposure for Sq-1G-900-1F-1h-L. The temperature of Sq-2G-900-1F-1h-L was lower by 43.15% and 52.81% for 30 and 60 min of fire. For Sq-1G-900-1F-2h-L and Sq-2G-900-1F-2h-L, the temperature reductions was 65.66%, 52.94%, 50.79 and 42.93, and 38.0%, 50.0%, 53.65% and 53.92%, for 30, 60, 90, and 120 min of fire exposure, respectively.

Fig. 9. Temperature values comparison in T5 with time.

Fig. 10. Temperature values comparison in T5 with time.

Fig. 11. Temperature comparison for 120 min duration.

Fig. 12. Temperature comparison for 60 min duration.

The thermal behavior and performance of the gypsum were significantly influenced by its moisture content, as it dissociates and evaporates at elevated temperatures [7]. Therefore, the thermal properties of gypsum are temperature-dependent. Gypsum shrinkage at high temperatures is the main cause of the structural failure of gypsum layers in a fire. Gypsum shrinks at varying rates depending on the thickness of the layer due to the non-uniform temperature that causes thermal strains along it. As gypsum loses strength at high temperatures, the mechanical stresses caused by the restrained thermal strains eventually cause cracks. Fire resistance of

gypsum board assemblies is considerably affected by gypsum fall-off in the fire. As a result, gypsum manufacturers are constantly looking for ways to make their gypsum board products more structurally effective. It is sensible to investigate whether gypsum products with reduced shrinkage rates perform better structurally in fire-related situations [6].

C. Axial Displacements

The axial displacements measured by the dial gauges can trace their evolution in time. Figure 13 shows a comparison of the obtained axial displacements. The axial displacements increased to a maximum and then decreased under the axis of the initial position. Initially, due to high temperatures, the column elongates and then shrinks with the degradation of the mechanical properties of concrete and reinforcing steel. The

axis of the initial position is not crossed at the same time as the restraining forces because their relationship with the column's axial displacement is non-linear. The axial displacement values vary due to the high temperature, indicated as positive and negative values. The maximum axial displacements of the coated specimens were approximately 3.85 and 5.3 mm, respectively, for the side exposed directly to the fire flame, as shown in Table IV and Figure 13(a)-(b). In the coated specimens, the axial displacements were taken by two dial gauges on the top (exposed to direct fire flame) and bottom (non-exposed) sides. Figure 13 (c)-(f) shows that the maximum axial displacements were 2.5, 4.687, 0.91, and 0.43 mm, for the specimens exposed to direct fire flame and 1.46, 3.58, 2.67, and 1.195 mm for indirect heating flow.

TABLE III. RESULTS AFTER THE TIME OF FIRE EXPOSURE FOR ALL COLUMNS TEST

Column reference	Gypsum layer thickness (mm)	Time of exposure to fire (min)	T5 max (°C)	(T-surface) max (°C)	$((T_R - T_G) / T_R) \%$	$((T_{surf} - T_G) / T_{surf}) \%$	$\Theta_{rebar-max}$ (°C)	Rebar-Heat reduction %	ALmax (mm)		Spalling observation
									Top	Bottom	
Sq-R-900-1F-1h-L	0	60	642	900	0	0	342	0	3.85	*	yes
Sq-R-900-1F-2h-L	0	120	800	900	0	0	382	0	5.3	*	yes
Sq-1G-900-1F-1h-L	10	60	176	422	72.52	53.11	112	67.25	2.5	1.46	No
Sq-1G-900-1F-2h-L	10	120	313	451	60.87	49.88	219	42.67	4.687	3.58	No
Sq-2G-900-1F-1h-L	20	60	132	342	79.43	62.00	109	68.12	0.91	2.67	No
Sq-2G-900-1F-2h-L	20	120	235	373	70.62	58.55	176	53.92	0.43	1.195	No

(*) not recorded

Fig. 13. Time-axial displacement due to high temperature.

V. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

Unprotected reinforced concrete parts exposed to extreme heat behave differently from the coated ones. The results of this study showed that the use of a gypsum plaster layer to protect reinforced concrete columns exposed to direct fire flame reduced one third the amount of heat penetrated during the period of higher exposure compared to unprotected ones. The gaps in the plaster material dissipate the heat reaching the body of the column and, therefore, the residual heat penetrates the section-cross of the column down to the core area, as well as the presence of moisture content in the plaster can reduce the effect of heat for a certain period.

CREDIT AUTHOR STATEMENT

Abdul Muttalib I.Said: Conceptualization, methodology, writing, review, and editing. Mohanad Salih Farhan: Writing the original draft preparation and carrying out the experimental tests.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Norsk, A. Sauca, and K. Livkiss, "Fire resistance evaluation of gypsum plasterboard walls using machine learning method," *Fire Safety Journal*, vol. 130, Jun. 2022, Art. no. 103597, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.firesaf.2022.103597>.
- [2] R. Prielor *et al.*, "Modelling approach to predict the fire-related heat transfer in porous gypsum based on multi-phase simulations including water vapour transport, phase change and radiative heat transfer," *Applied Thermal Engineering*, vol. 206, Apr. 2022, Art. no. 118013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2021.118013>.
- [3] J. Zehfuß and L. Sander, "Gypsum plasterboards under natural fire—Experimental investigations of thermal properties," *Civil Engineering Design*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 62–72, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1002/cend.202100002>.
- [4] J. R. Mehoff, P. Cuerrier, and G. Carisse, "A model for predicting heat transfer through gypsum-board/wood-stud walls exposed to fire," *Fire and Materials*, vol. 18, no. 5, pp. 297–305, 1994, <https://doi.org/10.1002/fam.810180505>.
- [5] P. A. G. Piloto, S. Rodríguez-del-Río, and D. Vergara, "Fire Analysis of Timber-Framed Walls Lined with Gypsum," *Materials*, vol. 15, no. 3, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 741, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma15030741>.
- [6] I. Rahmanian, "Thermal and mechanical properties of gypsum boards and their influences on fire resistance of gypsum board based systems," Ph.D. dissertation, University of Manchester, Manchester, UK, 2011.
- [7] R. S. Warwar and A. I. Said, "Mechanical Properties of Normal Strength Concrete Covered with Gypsum Layers and Exposed to High Temperatures (Fire Flame)," in *Geotechnical Engineering and Sustainable Construction*, Singapore, 2022, pp. 641–656, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-6277-5_51.
- [8] R. S. Warwar and A. I. Said, "Flexural Behavior of Reinforced Concrete Beams Covered by Gypsum Layers and Exposed to Elevated Temperatures," in *E3S Web of Conferences - Second International Conference on Geotechnical Engineering*, Iraq, 2021, vol. 318, Art. no. 03005, <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202131803005>.
- [9] "Standard Test Method for Static Modulus of Elasticity and Poisson's Ratio of Concrete in Compression," American Society for Testing and Materials, West Conshohocken, PA, USA, Standard ASTM C469-02, 2002.
- [10] ACI Committee 318, "Building Code Requirements for Structural Concrete (ACI 318-19) - Commentary (ACI 318R-19)," American Concrete Institute, Farmington Hills, MI, USA, ACI 318R-19, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.14359/51716937>.
- [11] "Standard Test Methods for Determining Effects of Large Hydrocarbon Pool Fires on Structural Members and Assemblies" American Society for Testing and Materials, West Conshohocken, PA, USA, Standard ASTM E1529-22.
- [12] A. M. Al-Hilali, A. F. Izzet, and N. Oukaili, "Static Shear Strength of a Non-Prismatic Beam with Transverse Openings," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 8349–8353, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4789>.
- [13] A. J. Daraj and A. H. Al-Zuhairi, "The Combined Strengthening Effect of CFRP Wrapping and NSM CFRP Laminates on the Flexural Behavior of Post-Tensioning Concrete Girders Subjected to Partially Strand Damage," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 8856–8863, Aug. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5008>.
- [14] H. Q. Abbas and A. H. Al-Zuhairi, "Flexural Strengthening of Prestressed Girders with Partially Damaged Strands Using Enhancement of Carbon Fiber Laminates by End Sheet Anchorages," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 8884–8890, Aug. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5007>.

The Incorporation of Thermocouples in Knitted Structures

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ABSTRACT

Recent developments in textiles have led to the manufacturing of a variety of fabrics. These developments include spacer fabrics, embroidered fabrics, embedded sensors in fabrics, ECG vests, etc. Electronic components are also being knit within fabrics. The study used a configuration of thermocouples, based on the Seebeck effect, knitted into the main structure using a variety of yarn filaments. The knitted fabric was tested against temperature variation to examine how it affects the impedance of the knitted thermocouples. The testing procedure produced promising results, as it showed that certain combinations of knitting materials may result in positive and negative temperature coefficients of the fabric. The combination of the tested materials provides a guide to developing similar structures for thermoelectric sensor applications.

Keywords-knitted fabric; Seebeck effect; technical textiles; thermocouple; temperature sensing

I. INTRODUCTION

Washable and reusable fabrics have been developed in the form of embedded sensors or a combination of embedded and printed electrodes [1-4]. These fabrics have the advantages of individuality and adaptability to varying climatic conditions and are useful in postoperative, athletics, firefighting, law enforcement, and other conditions [5]. In [6], an approach for a temperature-measuring fabric was presented by encapsulating a commercially available thermistor in knitting yarns. Another scientific approach is to embed temperature sensors in knitting fabrics to measure the temperature of human skin [6-8]. This was part of a series of temperature-sensing electronic fabrics, including armbands, socks, and glove-knit electrodes. In [9], such fabrics were developed and tested under a variety of loading mechanisms, such as stress-compressed. Many developments have been reported in several areas of technical textiles. In [10], a built-in fabric sensor was presented that was able to measure variations in basic parameters such as force, pressure, water content, and thermal activity. Although the material developed remained customizable, there was a trade-off to its robustness compared to the classical family of such sensors. In [11], the materials used for temperature sensing in technical textiles were discussed following the Seebeck effect and the principle of the Peltier effect. In [12], a set of wearable textiles was developed using a range of silver-coated conductive yarns with varied specifications. The behavior of knitted textile impedances developed as a result of knitted fabric using yarns doped with conducting materials was investigated, and the electrothermal performance was calculated to suggest the use of optimum fabric for use in electrothermal garments and other applications.

In [13], several metal-doped filament yarns were used to knit a fabric that would be used as a shield against

electromagnetic radiation. In [14], a weft-knitted fabric structure was developed using silver-coated yarn and lycra, based on the variation in resistance values in a variety of knitted fabrics. In [15], a fabric for temperature sensing the human body was developed, using standard available temperature sensors embedded in the fabric during the knitting process. In [16], a knitted glove was presented that incorporated embedded sensors of metal-coated yarn with a base of non-conducting ordinary yarn to respond as strain gauges. The glove was tested for pattern recognition of hand gestures, and the experimental procedure was mainly based on the resistance variation of the developed sensor, which is the basis for a standard strain gauge. In [17], a low-profile knitted antenna was presented for use in wireless body area networks in a bandwidth range of 1.4 GHz. In [18], a wearable antenna was presented and its dielectric properties were tested, focusing on the behavior of the antenna when bent at a certain radius. In [19], flexible strain sensors were presented within a knit structure and tested for human motion detection in a 3D setup. The experimental results showed that it produced very close to realistic human motion sensing. In [20], knitted sensors were used to monitor the body and its surrounding temperature.

In 1834, Peltier discovered that in a junction between two dissimilar metals, a flow of current was established when the junction was subjected to a hot or cold situation. Figure 1 shows a basic standard set-up of a thermocouple. The equation governing such an arrangement is given by:

$$\Delta U = \alpha(\Delta T)$$

where ΔU is the difference in the Seebeck coefficient of two metals and ΔT is the temperature difference between the hot and cold junctions.

Fig. 1. Thermocouple model and signal conditioning.

The current study used conducting yarns to act as a basic Thermocouple (TC) knitted arrangement. These TCs act as an array of temperature-sensing elements at each junction of knitted stitches. Therefore, they are capable of sensing temperature variations in their vicinity or on the surface to which they are subjected. The TC can easily be adjusted to become a part of any knitted structure. The two basic yarns act as scaffolds for the knit structure and have different enrichment metals doped into them. Therefore, when these yarns are incorporated into a knit structure, they act as a loose form of a thermocouple junction. This suffices for the appearance of impedance variation at the output terminals of the fabric. This variation in impedance is a function of change in temperature. The change can be linear or exponential, depending on the choice of the conducting yarns. In addition to basic developments in technical textiles, a high number of applied fields have been explored in this area.

II. DESCRIPTION

Basic knit structures can be used in various combinations and beneficial ways. This can be achieved using a variety of conducting and semiconducting material-enriched filament yarns. In basic categories of knitting, there are the weft and warp knitting methods. Figure 2 shows the simplest weft-knitted structure, while Figure 3 shows a tuck loop within the weft-knit. This is the very loop used for the realization of the fabric under consideration.

Fig. 2. Basic weft knit.

Fig. 3. A tuck loop within weft knit.

A range of platforms can be used to insert conducting wires and filaments in a knit structure, ranging from single-layer to multiple-layer fabrics, depending on the cause and target application. However, this study used a single-layer setup. The samples were knit on a flatbed machine with a modified feed arrangement, as shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Flatbed machine with side feed arrangement.

A range of metal yarns and filaments were used to knit fabric samples. These materials were procured from various manufacturing resources and supplied in the form of small spools or reels. It was not feasible to use them as such on the knitting machine due to various reasons, such as repeated wire breaks due to friction with the flanges of the spools and the tension in the wire. Each sample was developed in such a way that the combination of wire/filament was sufficient to withstand the Seebeck effect. The Seebeck effect is supposed to work very effectively when there is a strong connection/conductive bonding between two different metals. However, in the experiment, a loose connection between the two metals was inevitable because of the knitting process. This led to some promising results, whereas, the connection between the two yarns was in the loose form. This idea was incorporated into the knit structures using a few combinations of metal and metal-enriched yarns. These yarns were used as part of knitted structures, as shown in Figures 5-9.

Fig. 5. A sample using stainless steel and tungsten yarns.

Fig. 6. A sample using two tungsten yarns of varying diameter.

Fig. 7. Silver enriched yarn with stainless steel wire of 0.15 mm diameter.

Fig. 8. Stainless steel yarn and wire of 0.15 mm diameter.

Fig. 9. Silver and nickel-coated yarns.

Due to the knit pattern, both metal yarns had a loose connection to each other, so each crossing of the yarns acted as a loose thermocouple. These loose connections behave as a large number of thermocouples connected in a series arrangement. Therefore, a small change in impedance occurs at each junction, which then adds up to show a considerable change in the readings at the output terminals of the fabric. As a result, the knitted fabric by this technique has several advantages over the conventional thermocouple. The resulting fabric was washable, wearable, durable, and flexible, opening more avenues for thermocouple applications. The range of applications could range from very basic to sophisticated applications, such as those in the medical and sports fields.

III. THE EXPERIMENT

Several knit fabric samples were developed, with different metal yarns and knit patterns. The output terminals of each sample were connected directly to a digital Ohm meter. A Fisher Scientific hot plate was used for the gradual heating of each sample. Each sample was covered with a plane piece of

ceramic when placed on the hot plate to provide rigidity and a uniform environment to the sample. Figure 10 shows the experimental setup. Each sample showed variations in the overall impedance of the incorporated thermocouples across the conducting leads, depending on the type of metal used. The overall impedance of conducting junctions in the samples was the result of temperature variation.

Fig. 10. Experimental arrangement for fabric heating up.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A selection of metal-enriched yarns and thin wires was used to knit a total of 10 samples. Each sample was tested for its response to temperature variation. The samples were chosen for their good response to thermal variation.

Figure 11 shows the results for a knit combination of fine stainless steel and tungsten wires. Due to the nature of the combination, a limitation in the temperature range was found. A nearly linear relationship between the temperature and the observed impedance was observed. The temperature range covered in this case was 31-73°C. The impedance response was stable in certain temperature ranges. However, the largest span of impedance stability was in the temperature range of 35-38°C.

Fig. 11. Combination of stainless steel and tungsten wires for knit sample.

Figure 12, shows the results obtained using tungsten wires for both conductors. However, the diameter chosen for the two conductors was different, as mentioned in the title of the figure. In this case, the results were very encouraging compared to those obtained in Figure 11, as it shows more linearity in the impedance variation for temperature changes. The temperature range covered in this case was 35-90°C.

Fig. 12. Tungsten wires used for both conductors.

Figure 13 presents the results for a knit sample using a combination of stainless steel and silver-enriched yarns. In the experiment, 50% of the junctions were bonded using conductive adhesive. The variation in impedance was observed to be linear. However, dips in the plot appear due to the flexibility of the filament yarns at the junction of the two metals.

Fig. 13. Combination of stainless steel and silver-enriched yarns.

The combination of stainless steel enriched yarn and 27% nickel-coated copper filament was tried. Two knit structures were developed for this combination. The first was a complete knitting pattern and the other had a pattern with a miss out of 3 stitches. Figures 14 and 15 show the excellent linear relationship between temperature and impedance in both cases.

Fig. 14. Combination of stainless steel-enriched yarn and nickel-coated copper wire in a complete knit sample.

Fig. 15. Combination of stainless steel enriched yarn and nickel-coated copper wire in the 3 missed-out stitches in the knit sample.

A further combination was tried to achieve a good linear relationship between temperature and impedance variation, using silver-enriched yarn and nickel-coated copper wire. In this case, a round trip of temperature variation was carried out. Figure 16 shows the results.

Fig. 16. Combination of silver-enriched yarn and nickel-coated copper wire in the knit sample.

The data obtained from the custom knit samples show that their performance was very satisfactory in terms of the aim of this study. The performance of the incorporated thermocouples is great compared to that of the investigations discussed in the introduction of this article. The novelty of this work is the flexibility, durability, and washability of the thermocouples compared to the classical ones, which are rigid in physical nature, thus making their application difficult in specialized situations in general engineering and medical applications. In the medical field, such samples can be easily used to avoid bed sore situations.

V. CONCLUSION

The materials used to develop the samples showed diverse responses to the subjected temperature changes. This experimental study was conducted to collect consistent data. However, the samples worked based on positive and negative temperature coefficients. The establishment of the coefficient

in the positive or negative direction was due to the choice of combination of metals used in the samples. The results of the knit structures were found to be satisfactory. This study can be used as a guide for developing thermosensitive knit structures. Such structures are long-lasting and can be used for temperature sensing in various applications that have access difficulties, such as medical, sports, and other high-tech fields.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. V. Nicholas and D. R. White, *Traceable Temperatures - An Introduction to Temperature Measurement and Calibration*, 2nd ed. Chichester UK, 2001.
- [2] D. Marculescu *et al.*, "Electronic textiles: A platform for pervasive computing," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 91, no. 12, pp. 1995–2018, Sep. 2003, <https://doi.org/10.1109/JPROC.2003.819612>.
- [3] C. Ataman *et al.*, "Humidity and Temperature Sensors on Plastic Foil for Textile Integration," *Procedia Engineering*, vol. 25, pp. 136–139, Jan. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2011.12.034>.
- [4] A. Satharasinghe, T. Hughes-Riley, and T. Dias, "A Review of Solar Energy Harvesting Electronic Textiles," *Sensors*, vol. 20, no. 20, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 5938, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s20205938>.
- [5] J. F. Gu, S. Gorgutsa, and M. Skorobogatiy, "Soft capacitor fibers for electronic textiles," *Applied Physics Letters*, vol. 97, no. 13, Sep. 2010, Art. no. 133305, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3488351>.
- [6] P. Lugoda *et al.*, "Flexible Temperature Sensor Integration into E-Textiles Using Different Industrial Yarn Fabrication Processes," *Sensors*, vol. 20, no. 1, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 73, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s20010073>.
- [7] P. Lugoda, T. Hughes-Riley, C. Oliveira, R. Morris, and T. Dias, "Developing Novel Temperature Sensing Garments for Health Monitoring Applications," *Fibers*, vol. 6, no. 3, Sep. 2018, Art. no. 46, <https://doi.org/10.3390/fib6030046>.
- [8] A. M. Shahidi, T. Hughes-Riley, C. Oliveira, and T. Dias, "An Investigation of the Physical and Electrical Properties of Knitted Electrodes When Subjected to Multi-Axial Compression and Abrasion," *Proceedings*, vol. 68, no. 1, 2021, Art. no. 2, <https://doi.org/10.3390/proceedings2021068002>.
- [9] L. Michalski, K. Eckersdorf, J. Kucharski, and J. McGhee, *Temperature Measurement*. Chichester, UK: John Wiley & Sons, 2001.
- [10] L. M. Castano and A. B. Flatau, "Smart fabric sensors and e-textile technologies: a review," *Smart Materials and Structures*, vol. 23, no. 5, Dec. 2014, Art. no. 053001, <https://doi.org/10.1088/0964-1726/23/5/053001>.
- [11] K. Chatterjee and T. K. Ghosh, "Thermoelectric Materials for Textile Applications," *Molecules*, vol. 26, no. 11, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 3154, <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26113154>.
- [12] K. Sun, S. Liu, and H. Long, "Structural Parameters Affecting Electrothermal Properties of Woolen Knitted Fabrics Integrated with Silver-Coated Yarns," *Polymers*, vol. 11, no. 10, Oct. 2019, Art. no. 1709, <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym11101709>.
- [13] F. G. K. Abdulla and R. Abdulla, "A Comparative Application for Evaluating Composite Fabrics Used in Electromagnetic Shielding," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 2156–2159, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1480>.
- [14] O. Atalay, S. Kursun Bahadır, F. Kalaoglu, and S. Vassiliadis, "Development of Textile-Based Temperature Sensor," presented at the 5th International Istanbul Textile Congress 2015: Innovative Technologies "Inspire to Innovate," Istanbul, Turkey, Sep. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.1870.3125>.
- [15] R. Hudec, S. Matuska, P. Kamencay, and L. Hudecova, "Concept of a Wearable Temperature Sensor for Intelligent Textile," *Advances in Electrical and Electronic Engineering*, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 92–98, Jun. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.15598/aeec.v18i2.3610>.
- [16] S. Lee, Y. Choi, M. Sung, J. Bae, and Y. Choi, "A Knitted Sensing Glove for Human Hand Postures Pattern Recognition," *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 4, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 1364, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s21041364>.
- [17] W. Bouamra, I. Sfar, A. Mersani, L. Osman, and J. M. Ribero, "A Low-Profile Wearable Textile Antenna Using AMC for WBAN Applications at 5.8GHz," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 9048–9055, Aug. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5011>.
- [18] S. Mallavarapu and A. Lokam, "Circuit Modeling and Analysis of Wearable Antennas on the Effect of Bending for Various Feeds," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 8180–8187, Feb. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4699>.
- [19] Y. Li, X. Miao, J. Y. Chen, G. Jiang, and Q. Liu, "Sensing performance of knitted strain sensor on two-dimensional and three-dimensional surfaces," *Materials & Design*, vol. 197, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 109273, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2020.109273>.
- [20] Y. Peng and Y. Cui, "Advanced Textiles for Personal Thermal Management and Energy," *Joule*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 724–742, Apr. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2020.02.011>.
- [21] W. Göpel, J. Hesse, and J. N. Zemel, *Sensors - Thermal Sensors*, vol. 4. Weinheim, Germany: VCH, 1990.

Utilization of Solar Energy for Electric Vehicle Charging and the Energy Consumption of Residential Buildings in Northern Cyprus: A Case Study

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ABSTRACT

Solar energy represents an opportunity to facilitate the operation of Electric Vehicle (EV) charging stations and cover the energy demand of households, contributing to sustainability and reducing carbon emissions. In light of the emerging need for solar energy as a source of electricity generation for building and charging electric vehicles, this study aimed to assess the technical and economic feasibility of using photovoltaic (PV) systems to generate electricity for residential buildings and meet the changing needs of EVs to reduce energy demand on the grid. To achieve this objective, monthly solar radiation data were collected from the NASA power dataset to assess solar radiation levels in the region and determine the suitability and potential for harnessing solar energy for various applications. The results showed that northern Cyprus has exceptionally abundant and consistently stable solar energy resources. The daily energy for selected residential households and the GÜNSEL B9 and J9 electric cars was estimated to determine the capacity of the required PV systems. In addition, information was collected on the prices of solar panels, inverters, energy storage systems, etc., which were taken into account to evaluate the economic viability of the developed systems. The results demonstrate that the use of solar energy to charge EVs and meet the energy demands of households is technically viable and economically feasible. The use of electric cars offers nearly double the advantages compared to conventional fuel-powered ones, making them a more environmentally sustainable option.

Keywords-northern Cyprus; solar energy; techno-economic feasibility, electric vehicle; GÜNSEL B9; GÜNSEL J9; energy demand

I. INTRODUCTION

Transportation plays a crucial role in all societies, facilitating lifestyle and enabling the delivery of goods and services that contribute to societal progress. As global efforts to promote sustainable development patterns continue, various strategies have emerged to enhance the sustainability of transportation. These strategies encompass advances in vehicle technology and the adoption of clean fuels. Consequently, the

transportation system holds significant importance in fostering the balanced development of a country's economic and social systems. However, a major challenge for the global transport system is its heavy reliance on fossil fuels, particularly oil and gas [1]. Approximately one-third of the total final energy consumption stems from the transport sector, encompassing both passenger and freight travel, which predominantly rely on fossil fuel sources [2].

Oil is the primary energy source for transportation, accounting for 94% of the total energy demand in the sector, while natural gas and other fuels contribute 3%, biofuels 2%, and electricity 1% [3]. These non-renewable fossil fuels have the significant drawback of emitting substantial amounts of harmful pollutants, including sulfur dioxide, nitrogen oxides, and especially carbon dioxide when burned [4]. These emissions are directly involved in the pressing issue of global warming [4]. As a result, there has been a growing focus on the electrification of mobility as a means to address these emission concerns. Recently, substantial efforts have been made to assess the impacts and present approaches to reduce pollutant emissions from on-road traffic and the subsequent effects on air quality [5-7]. Currently, the primary objectives of these initiatives are: (a) to reduce emissions per vehicle by implementing cleaner fuels and technologies, such as renewable fuels or biofuels, natural gas vehicles, and fuel cell vehicles, and (b) to adopt mobility management strategies that aim to decrease the overall speed of traffic circulation. By pursuing these methods, there is a concerted effort to mitigate the harmful environmental effects associated with transportation and pave the way for a more sustainable and environmentally friendly mobility system. The adoption of Electric Vehicles (EVs) offers several potential advantages, depending on the type of power plant that generates electricity for them. EVs can lead to improvements in energy efficiency and reduce energy dependence, fossil fuel consumption, and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions [8]. However, it is important to consider that the environmental benefits of EVs are influenced by the composition of the electricity-power mix [9]. Although EVs themselves produce zero tailpipe emissions, the overall emissions associated with their use depend on the sources of electricity used for charging. If electricity comes from renewable sources, such as wind, solar, or hydroelectric power, the emissions and environmental impact can be significantly reduced.

Solar energy has emerged as a highly promising renewable energy source for powering EV charging stations [10]. Solar power systems use PV technology to convert sunlight into electricity. Solar energy offers several advantages for EV charging. At first, it is a renewable source, meaning that it is virtually inexhaustible and does not deplete over time. This reduces the dependence on finite fossil fuel resources and contributes to a more sustainable energy system [11]. Additionally, solar power systems produce electricity with minimal environmental impact, since they do not emit GHG or pollutants during operation, resulting in reduced carbon emissions and improved air quality. This is in line with the goals of mitigating climate change and reducing the overall environmental footprint. Solar energy can also provide greater energy independence. By generating electricity on-site through solar panels installed at EV charging stations, there is less dependence on the traditional electricity grid and external energy sources [12]. This can enhance energy resilience and reduce vulnerability to power outages or fluctuations in the energy supply. In addition, solar-powered EV charging stations can be strategically located in areas with ample sunlight, such as parking lots, highways, or urban spaces. This enables convenient and accessible charging options for EV owners

while using underutilized spaces for renewable energy generation. Integration of solar energy into the EV charging infrastructure contributes to a cleaner and more sustainable transportation system. As solar technology continues to advance and become more affordable, it has significant potential to reduce the environmental impact of EV charging and promote the widespread adoption of EVs.

The energy sector of northern Cyprus relies heavily on imported fossil fuels, exposing it to fluctuations in global fuel prices and geopolitical uncertainties that can affect energy security and affordability. Northern Cyprus has a significant potential for renewable energy sources, including solar energy [13-19], as it has abundant sunshine throughout the year, which can be used to diversify the energy mix and reduce dependence on imported fossil fuels. Furthermore, the favorable climate makes it suitable for solar installations, both for utility-scale projects and distributed solar systems on rooftops. This study investigated the techno-economic viability of implementing PV with energy storage systems in northern Cyprus. The system was designed for home use, primarily focusing on charging an owner's EV and meeting the energy needs of the house. The main goal was to improve the use of PV energy for EV charging and household consumption, reducing the dependence on grid power. The incorporation of an energy storage system enables the use of stored energy during unfavorable conditions, ensuring uninterrupted EV charging regardless of weather or time of day. By integrating PV generation, energy storage, and EV charging, the system aimed to maximize solar energy use while minimizing dependence on grid electricity. This approach promotes sustainability and offers potential economic benefits by lowering electricity costs and reducing dependence on external energy sources.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

A. The GÜNSEL Electric Car

GÜNSEL is an electric car developed in northern Cyprus. Its development began in 2016. The project aimed to create a car that would be environmentally friendly, cost-effective, and meet the needs of the modern driver. The GÜNSEL electric car is a sleek and stylish vehicle powered by a lithium-ion battery located underneath. The battery can be charged using a standard electrical outlet or a dedicated charging station. The GÜNSEL electric car has a range of up to 350 km on a single charge, which is more than enough for most drivers. It can reach a top speed of 170 km/h and can go from 0 to 100 km/h in just 8 s. The car is equipped with a variety of advanced features, including a touchscreen display that provides access to different functions, such as music, navigation, and climate control. The car also has a variety of safety features, including lane departure warning, automatic emergency braking, and adaptive cruise control. The GÜNSEL electric car has a low-slung profile that gives it a sporty appearance. Its interior is spacious and comfortable, with plenty of legroom and headroom for passengers. Seats are upholstered in high-quality materials and the dashboard is designed to be easy to read and use. The GÜNSEL electric car is environmentally friendly and cost-effective.

B. The Intensity of Sunlight in Northern Cyprus

To assess the potential success of solar-powered Battery Electric Car (BEC) charging stations, it is essential to initially assess the solar energy resource throughout the country. Solar energy is one of the most abundant, clean, affordable, and sustainable energy resources, particularly in arid or semi-arid regions. In general, global solar radiation is defined by the Global Horizontal Irradiance (GHI) and Diffused Horizontal Irradiance (DHI) [20]. GHI is a significant factor to assess energy generation for flat-plate PVs. Figure 1 shows the long-term average of solar resources, including GHI generated by the Global Solar Atlas. PV power potential is a comprehensive assessment of the power generation capabilities of renewable energy sources that represents the average yearly and daily potential energy generation from a 1 kW solar PV plant over a long period, as shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 1. GHI map of Cyprus.

Fig. 2. PV power potential map.

C. Dataset

This study evaluated the solar potential in 33 selected regions distributed over northern Cyprus. Table I shows geographic information including latitude (Lat), longitude (Long), and elevation (El) above sea level of the selected locations. The lack of availability of high-quality meteorological data has led to the use of satellite-generated or

interpolated synthetic meteorological data available in grids with various spatiotemporal resolutions [21]. Several studies have evaluated the potential of solar energy at specific locations using satellite data such as the NASA Power Dataset [22-24]. The NASA POWER dataset is a comprehensive set of meteorological data used for research and analysis of renewable energy resources, particularly solar and wind energy that contains hourly, daily, and monthly data on a range of meteorological variables, such as solar radiation and wind speed [25]. Monthly data, including GHI and Air Temperature (AT), were used to assess the economic feasibility of solar PVs to generate electricity as a power source for the 33 selected locations shown in Table I. It can be observed that the solar radiation levels remain consistent throughout the region. This suggests that any part of the region has the potential to establish a solar-powered charging station. The uniformity of radiation levels also implies that a single charging station design could be implemented effectively in various geographic regions of northern Cyprus, as the annual GHI values ranged from 1704.07 kWh/m² to 1948.00 kWh/m². The minimum and maximum GHI were recorded in Beylerbeyi and Ercan, respectively. Figure 3 shows that the lowest and highest GHI were recorded in December and June. Table I also lists the optimum orientation angles in terms of Slope (S) and Azimuth (A), which were found using the PVGIS simulation tool [18].

TABLE I. INFORMATION ON THE SELECTED AREAS

Location	El [m]	Lat [°N]	Long [°E]	GHI [kWh/m ²]	AT [°C]	S [°]	A [°]
Akdeniz	89.0	35.3	33.0	1914.0	20.7	31.0	2.0
Camlibel	277.0	35.3	33.1	1918.4	19.5	31.0	3.0
Lapta	168.0	35.3	33.2	1865.3	19.2	29.0	-5.0
Girne	10.0	35.3	33.3	1920.6	19.5	31.0	-1.0
Beylerbeyi	225.0	35.3	33.4	1704.1	19.9	28.0	-22.0
Bogaz	300.0	35.3	33.3	1919.0	19.7	31.0	0.0
Tatlisu	168.0	35.2	33.5	1944.5	20.1	32.0	-3.0
Kantara	480.0	35.4	33.9	1877.8	20.3	31.0	-4.0
Esentepe	183.0	35.3	33.6	1925.8	20.0	31.0	0.0
Guzelyurt	52.0	35.2	33.0	1929.5	19.5	31.0	0.0
Gaziveren	19.0	35.2	32.9	1930.0	19.5	31.0	0.0
Lefke	129.0	35.1	32.8	1925.1	16.3	30.0	-8.0
Yesilirmak	20.0	35.2	32.7	1916.1	18.2	30.0	-2.0
Ercan	119.0	35.2	33.5	1948.0	20.4	32.0	-4.0
Serdarli	111.0	35.3	33.6	1920.3	20.5	32.0	-5.0
Degirmenlik	168.0	35.3	33.5	1916.3	20.1	31.0	-1.0
Gecitkale	45.0	35.2	33.7	1946.5	20.8	32.0	-2.0
Gonendere	75.0	35.3	33.7	1924.8	20.5	32.0	-3.0
Vadili	54.0	35.1	33.7	1947.0	20.7	32.0	-2.0
Beyarmudu	87.0	35.0	33.7	1946.9	20.7	31.0	0.0
Cayirova	67.0	35.3	34.0	1910.4	20.5	31.0	2.0
Iskele	39.0	35.3	33.9	1923.8	21.0	31.0	0.0
Mehmetcik	99.0	35.4	34.1	1910.2	20.5	31.0	2.0
Gazimagusa	10.0	35.1	33.9	1941.6	21.0	31.0	2.0
Salamis	6.0	35.2	33.9	1941.7	21.0	31.0	1.0
Alevkaya	623.0	35.3	33.5	1925.4	20.2	31.0	2.0
Zumrutkoy	129.0	35.2	33.0	1933.9	19.5	31.0	0.0
Alaykoy	166.0	35.2	33.3	1925.4	19.8	32.0	-2.0
Lefkosa	134.0	35.2	33.4	1945.4	20.1	32.0	-3.0
Ziyamet	82.0	35.5	34.1	1908.1	20.3	30.0	3.0
Dipkarpaz	136.0	35.6	34.4	1896.1	20.5	31.0	5.0
Yenierenkoy	123.0	35.5	34.2	1893.4	20.8	31.0	5.0
Dortyol	54.0	35.2	33.8	1942.4	21.0	32.0	-1.0

Fig. 3. Monthly GHI value for northern Cyprus.

D. Solar PV System

A solar PV system harnesses sunlight through PV modules to generate electricity, which can be used directly, fed back into the grid, or stored in batteries. PV panels convert solar energy into DC electricity, have a lifespan of 20 to 30 years, and are available in different technologies, such as monocrystalline silicon, polycrystalline silicon, etc. [17]. Inverters are essential components that convert the DC output to usable AC, ensuring safety and efficiency. Solar batteries store the excess electricity from PV systems, providing reliable power on cloudy days, at night, or during outages, enhancing sustainability, and allowing for a continuous energy supply [4, 17].

E. Power Demand by an EV

The power consumption of an EV is influenced by several factors, including distance traveled, battery capacity, and driving mode. These variables play a significant role in determining electric vehicle power consumption (P_D) [11]. The following equations were used to estimate P_D [26]:

$$P_D = \frac{K_d E_k}{T} \quad (1)$$

$$P_D = \frac{Q_{bat}(SOC_{max}-SOC)}{T} \quad (2)$$

where K_d is the number of km driven, E_k is the energy required per km, T is the time required to charge the vehicle battery, Q_{bat} is the battery capacity, SOC is the state of charge and SOC_{max} is the upper limit of the battery SOC. Consequently, the power demanded by EVs can be expressed using:

$$P = \sum_{i=1}^N P_{Di} \quad (3)$$

F. Inverter Sizing

Inverter sizing (SI) depends on two key factors: (1) the total wattage of the energy consumed (EC), and (2) the applied safety factor (SF). These considerations determine the appropriate size of the inverter required for the project.

$$SI = EC \times SF \quad (4)$$

G. Battery Sizing

Equation (5) can be employed to estimate the capacity of the battery for a PV project. For solar energy projects, it is recommended to utilize a deep cycle battery specifically designed for low energy level discharges [11]. The lead-acid battery serves as the foundation of the energy storage system and should be adequately sized to store enough energy to power an EV.

$$CB = \frac{ECN \times DA}{BE \times DD \times BNV} \quad (5)$$

where ECN is the energy consumption need, DA is the days of autonomy, BE is battery efficiency, DE is the depth of discharge, and BNV is the battery's nominal voltage.

H. Mathematical Modeling of Economic Viability

To calculate the cost of a solar plant for charging electric cars, several factors should be considered as follows:

- Determination of the power requirements: the power rating of the electric car charger can be estimated using :

$$P = VI \quad (6)$$

where P is the power rating in kW, V is the voltage in V, and I is the current in A.

- Energy consumption calculation (E): the amount of energy the charger will consume over a given time (t) can be found using:

$$E = P \times t \quad (7)$$

Note that the power consumption rate throughout the charging period was assumed to be constant. In reality, the power consumption may vary depending on the charging technology and the car's battery charging characteristics.

- Assessing solar plant capacity: Consider the average amount of sunlight available at the location. Solar panels have a capacity rating, usually given in W or kW. The number of solar panels (N_{sp}) needed was calculated based on the capacity required to generate the energy consumed by the charger as:

$$N_{sp} = \frac{E}{S_c \times SPF} \quad (8)$$

where S_c is the solar panel capacity in W and SPF is the solar panel efficiency in %.

- Calculation of the total energy generation: Estimate the total energy that the solar plant will generate annually using:

$$E_{total} = 365 \times S_c \times ASL \times SPF \quad (9)$$

where ASL is the average number of sunlight in hours/day.

- Determining the size of the solar plant (SPZ): The size of the solar plant in kW based on the total energy generation and the average number of sunlight is assessed by:

$$SPZ = \frac{E_{total}}{365 \times ASL} \quad (10)$$

This equation assumes consistent energy generation throughout the year and does not account for factors such as system losses, shading, and panel orientation.

- Calculation of the cost of the solar plant: The cost of a solar plant can vary depending on several factors, including the size, location, quality of the components, and installation costs.

- Consideration of additional costs: In addition to the solar plant itself, costs such as wiring, inverters, mounting structures, permits, and maintenance should be estimated.

I. The Energy Required for Household and EV

In this study, a typical household was selected to establish a load profile based on monthly electric bills, as shown in Figure 4. It was found that the average monthly energy demand was within the range of 482 (October) - 958 kWh (July) with an average value of 24.76 kWh/day. GÜNSEL B9 and J9 are electric vehicle models produced by GÜNSEL, and Table II shows their technical characteristics. Table III presents the main parameters of the battery used in GÜNSEL B9.

Fig. 4. Monthly energy demand for the selected household during 2022.

TABLE II. TECHNICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF GÜNSEL B9 AND J9

Electric Vehicle Model	B9	J9
Acceleration [km/h]	0-100	0-100
Charging Time [min]	30	30
Maximum Speed [m/s]	150	200
Maximum Power [kW]	140	280
Weight [kg]	1420	2000

TABLE III. TECHNICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF GÜNSEL B9 BATTERY PACK

Electric Vehicle Model	B9
Battery power capacity [Ah]	148
Nominal energy @ 0.2C [kWh]	52.6
Nominal voltage [V]	355
Maximum charge current [A]	125
Maximum discharge current [A]	350
Cell type	Li-ion cylindrical cell

In general, the daily energy required for an electric car can be estimated as shown below:

- Determination of the energy required (E_R) in kWh for a full charge by:

$$E_R = P_{max} \times C_t \tag{11}$$

where P_{max} is the maximum power of the car in kW and C_t is the charging time in h.

- Determination of the adjusted Energy required (AE_R) in kWh by:

$$AE_R = E_R \times C_e \tag{12}$$

where C_e is the charging efficiency percentage. Electric car charging is not 100% efficient, and there are losses during the charging process. Thus, it is assumed that $C_e = 90\%$.

- Calculation of the daily energy required (DE_R) in kWh/day:

$$DE_R = AE_R \times NC \tag{13}$$

where NC is the number of charges per day given by:

$$NC = \frac{\text{Daily Distance Traveled}}{B_{pc} \times B_f} \tag{14}$$

where B_{pc} is battery power capacity in kWh and B_f is battery efficiency in km/kWh. It should be noted that the battery efficiency for EVs was assumed to be 90%.

- The Charger Power (CP) of an EV can be estimated by:

$$CP = P_{max} \times \frac{\text{Range}}{S_{max}} \times \frac{B_{pc}}{\text{Range}} \tag{15}$$

where S_{max} is the maximum wind speed in km/h and $Range$ is in km. In general, the charging power of electric cars using a solar station can vary depending on several factors, including the capacity of the solar panels, the charging infrastructure, and the specific electric car model being charged [28-30]. In addition, charging power may also depend on other factors, such as the charging rate supported by the electric car's onboard charger and the compatibility between the charging station and the car [28]. In the literature, solar charging stations often have charging power capacities in the range of 3-22 kW per charging point. In this study, the charging power capacity was assumed to be 7, 11, and 22 kW.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Survey Results Related to Major Equipment Price Details

As there is a wide variety of PV modules and inverters available in the market, it is important to consider parameters such as cell type, system cost, warranty, and size [29]. Besides, it is significant to consider factors such as the output AC power, the efficiency of DC-AC conversion, and the capital cost for the selected suitable inverter. In this study, the economic and environmental analysis of installing a grid-connected PV system was conducted using the RETScreen software. It is important to note that the lowest GHI values of 1.66 kWh/m²/day and 2.53 kWh/m²/day were recorded at Beylerbeyi and Ercan, respectively, in December. Additionally, the maximum daily power consumption for a household is observed in July at 31 kWh/day. According to [29-30], the capacity of a PV system can be calculated by:

$$P_{max} = \frac{E_{AC} P_i}{G_{SR} f_{PV} \eta_{inv}} \tag{16}$$

where P_i is the solar radiation at STC in kW/m², G_{SR} is the global solar radiation (kWh/m²/d), f_{pv} is the PV derating factor, E_{AC} is the daily power consumption in kWh/d, and η_{inv} is the inverter yield.

Therefore, the PV capacity was estimated to be 32 kW, 36 kW, and 47 kW in Beylerbeyi, with an average value of 38 kW based on the lowest value of 1.66 kWh/m²/day. Based on the minimum GHI value in Ercan, the capacity of the PV plant was found to be 23, 27, and 38 kW with an average value of 30 kW. Table IV shows the specifications of the PV module used. In addition, a 40 kW pure sine wave inverter was selected, with an efficacy of 94% [17]. Moreover, the primary objective of the study was to reduce energy bills and meet energy requirements

for EVs and households. However, grid power will be used at night or on cloudy, overcast, and rainy days for the household, while the energy storage system will be used to power electric cars during the nighttime. Thus, by storing the excess solar energy generated during the day, electric car owners can rely on their own stored energy rather than solely relying on the grid. This promotes energy independence and reduces the dependence on external energy sources. The specification of the energy storage system is available in [28]. Table V provides the list prices for the selected equipment.

TABLE IV. SPECIFICATION OF USED PV PANEL

PV module Technology	Mono-si
Manufacturer	Jinko Solar
Model	JKM545M-72HL4
Maximum Power [W]	545.00
Maximum Power Voltage [V]	40.80
Maximum Power Current [A]	13.36
Open-circuit Voltage [V]	49.52
Short-circuit Current [A]	13.94
Module area [m ²]	2.58
Module Efficiency [%]	21.13
Warranty [Year]	25.00
Cost [USD/Wdc]	0.37

TABLE V. ECONOMIC PARAMETERS USED IN THIS STUDY

Parameter	Unit	Value
PV module cost	\$	202
Cost of 40kW inverter	\$	13990
Cost of 19.2kW energy storage system	\$	8430
Miscellaneous/contingency fund	% of the total initial cost	3
Installation and spare parts	% of the total initial cost	8
Feasibility study, development, and engineering cost	% of the total initial cost	0.6

B. Economic Feasibility of the Proposed System

For simplicity, a fixed solar tracking system was employed in this analysis. The economic feasibility of PV systems with various capacities was carried out using the RETScreen software. The initial financial parameters for the economic analysis were derived from the existing literature on the economic study of PV installations in northern Cyprus [30]. These sources provided relevant and reliable information on the financial aspects associated with PV projects in the region. Using these data, the economic analysis was able to incorporate the specific financial conditions and considerations relevant to PV installations in northern Cyprus [29]. RETScreen assists in the evaluation and optimization of renewable energy and energy efficiency projects and provides a comprehensive platform to conduct feasibility studies, assess energy production, calculate financial analysis, and evaluate the environmental impact of various project options. As mentioned above, the findings demonstrate that solar radiation levels remain uniform, indicating that any area of the region is suitable for a solar-powered charging station. This consistency in radiation levels also suggests the feasibility of implementing a single charging station design that would work effectively across different geographical regions in northern Cyprus. The energy generation of a solar PV system is influenced by the

solar radiation available at the location and the number of clear sunny days [31]. These factors directly impact both the annual energy exported to the grid by the panel and the capacity factor. Figure 5 illustrates the monthly variation of energy production for Beylerbeyi and Ercan, showing that maximum energy production occurs in July, while minimum energy production occurs in December. These variations in energy production throughout the year emphasize the importance of considering seasonal factors when evaluating the performance and planning the utilization of solar PC systems. Figure 6 shows the annual value of energy production at both selected locations. The annual values of the proposed systems were found to be in the range of 48528.1-71275.65 kWh for Beylerbeyi and 35094.12-57981.58 kWh for Ercan.

Fig. 5. Monthly variation of power generation from the PV system with different capacities: (a) Beylerbeyi and (b) Ercan.

Fig. 6. Annual value of energy generation from the PV system with different capacities.

The annual CF values were 17.31% for Beylerbeyi and 17.48% for Ercan. These results are supported by [29-34]. For example, in [31], it was found that the CF values were in the range of 17.54-27.42% for grid-connected PV systems that employed different sun-tracking modes. In [30], a CF of 16-23% was reported for the PV systems developed in Oman, while in [34], the CF values ranged between 15.37 and 15.75% for grid-connected PV systems using various technologies. Therefore, the annual energy production and the corresponding capacity factors at the selected locations meet the acceptable values. This implies that it is technically feasible to construct and operate solar PV plants in these locations considering the technical viability of the solar systems. These findings are valuable for decision-making processes related to renewable energy investments and further emphasize the suitability of solar energy as a viable and sustainable source of electricity. Furthermore, the economic viability of the proposed systems was explored. The economic assessment took financial metrics as input variables, including an inflation rate of 8%, a discount rate of 6%, a reinvestment rate of 9%, a debt ratio of 70%, a debt interest rate of 0%, and an electricity export escalation rate of 5%. The economic viability of a project is assessed using indicators such as Net Present Value (NPV), Internal Rate of Return (IRR), payback period, and Annual Life Cycle Savings (ALCS) [35-36]. Figures 7-8 illustrate the values of these indicators for Beylerbeyi and Ercan, respectively. The NPV, which represents the difference between the present value of cash inflows and outflows over a specified period, was found to be positive for the selected locations, indicating that the project is financially and economically feasible [35-37]. In addition, the IRR, a measure of project profitability, was determined to be higher than the required rate of return for the project at all locations [37]. According to [31, 37], to consider a project successful, it must be both fiscally and economically feasible. Additionally, the internal rate of return profitability assessment indicates that the projects at the selected sites are financially viable [4, 37]. Therefore, projects in these locations are economically viable compared to the required rate of return, which serves as the discount rate for the project. Based on these assessments, the projects in both locations are considered financially and economically acceptable. ALCS is a term commonly used to gauge the benefits of a project, calculated based on factors such as the net present value, project life, and discount rate. Figures 7-8 illustrate the results of ALCS, showing that they range between 4546.9 and 9705.8 USD/year. Furthermore, the payback period is a measure that indicates the time needed to recoup the initial investment made in a project through the net positive income. RETScreen considers two types of payback periods: equity payback and simple payback. Equity payback represents the time required to recover the initial investment considering only the equity portion. On the other hand, simple payback covers the entire investment, including both equity and debt. A shorter payback period is desirable as it signifies a faster return on investment. The payback period is a valuable tool to assess the risk associated with an investment, as it provides insight into the time frame required to recover the initial investment and helps evaluate the project's financial viability. The equity and simple payback periods were within the ranges of 2.4-2.9 years and 6.8-8.0 years, respectively.

Fig. 7. Economic performance of proposed PV systems for Beylerbeyi.

These findings indicate that the developed systems are financially feasible in all regions. In addition, the Electricity Production Cost (EPC) of the developed systems varies between 0.0371 and 0.0437 USD/kWh, as shown in Figures 7-8. The EPC values of the proposed systems fall within the respective ranges of [38]. This observation indicates that the established systems offer valuable information on the financial feasibility of the project in all regions.

Fig. 8. Economic performance of proposed PV systems for Ercan.

C. Comparison Between EVs and Fuel Cars

Several factors should be considered when measuring the savings in money from an electric car powered by a solar station compared to a fuel car, such as the energy consumption of the electric car, the energy required for a specific distance, the solar station's energy generation capacity, and the cost of electricity from the solar station. Before comparing EVs and fuel cars, this study considered the following assumptions:

- It was assumed that each BEC or fuel car would operate every day throughout the year. This assumption accounts for the possibility that both types of cars may require regular use and maintenance.
- The study did not consider the maintenance costs typically associated with the maintenance and repair of vehicles. Omitting these costs allowed for a simplified analysis that focused on other factors.
- The fuel price was assumed to remain constant at the current level, with a slight degree of variability of approximately 5%. This assumption acknowledged the potential for slight fluctuations in fuel prices but maintained a relatively stable reference point for comparison.

By establishing these assumptions, the study set the basis for evaluating the relative performance and costs of BECs and fuel cars while accounting for specific factors. Table VI lists the money savings from BEC powered by a solar station compared to a fuel car. It is a justifiable assertion that the implementation of renewable energy systems and the substitution of fuel cars for BECs is economically feasible.

TABLE VI. ECONOMIC PARAMETERS USED IN THIS STUDY

Variable	Model: B9	Model: J9
Range [km]	350.0	350.0
Energy Required [kWh/day]	465.8	941.9
Average of electricity production cost from the solar system in Beylerbeyi [USD/kWh]	0.0398	0.0398
Average of electricity production cost from the solar system in Ercan [USD/kWh]	0.0413	0.0413
Cost of charging the electric car [USD/year] in Beylerbeyi	6766.38	13683.12
Cost of charging the electric car [USD/year] in Ercan	7021.39	14198.82
Average litter required for fuel car [Lt]	44.16	44.16
Cost of fueling the car [USD/year]	15313.57	15313.57
Average savings [USD/year] in Beylerbeyi	8547.19	1630.45
Average savings [USD/year] in Ercan	8292.18	1114.75

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Solar projects have gained worldwide prominence as a means to shift from fossil fuel-based electricity generation to cleaner and renewable energy production. Their ability to promote economic growth, enhance energy security, and contribute to reducing greenhouse gas emissions has been widely recognized. This study assessed the economic viability of solar energy potential as a power source for households and EVs in northern Cyprus. Based on potential estimates, it was determined that Ercan was the most optimal location for the construction of PV plants. In addition, the feasibility analysis revealed promising results for using solar charging to power available EV types on the market and meet the energy demands of households. These findings are of particular significance for countries reliant on expensive and imported fuel. However, if the focus shifted solely to the use of solar power for EV charging without incorporating an energy storage system, the associated plant cost would be reduced by almost half and the relevance and viability of this study would be further enhanced. This study introduces a novel aspect by exploring the exclusive use of solar energy to generate electricity for households and

EVs, contributing a unique addition to existing studies. The robust technical foundation, economic feasibility, and environmentally sustainable implications of the study make it a valuable resource for policymakers in northern Cyprus.

Future research should be directed toward exploring the feasibility of charging battery electric vehicles using a hybrid system that combines solar and wind energy. This investigation aims to optimize the use of the most suitable renewable energy sources for EV charging while simultaneously meeting the energy demands of households throughout the day.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Zhao, K. Wang, X. Dong, and K. Dong, "Is smart transportation associated with reduced carbon emissions? The case of China," *Energy Economics*, vol. 105, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 105715, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2021.105715>.
- [2] "Eco-friendly transportation system in proposed permanent campus of American International University-Bangladesh," in *2017 6th International Conference on Clean Electrical Power (ICCEP)*, Santa Margherita Ligure, Italy, Jun. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCEP.2017.8004761>.
- [3] A. García-Olivares, J. Solé, and O. Osychenko, "Transportation in a 100% renewable energy system," *Energy Conversion and Management*, vol. 158, pp. 266–285, Feb. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2017.12.053>.
- [4] S. Rehman, M. A. Ahmed, M. H. Mohamed, and F. A. Al-Sulaiman, "Feasibility study of the grid connected 10MW installed capacity PV power plants in Saudi Arabia," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 80, pp. 319–329, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.05.218>.
- [5] P. Iodice and A. Senatore, "Atmospheric pollution from point and diffuse sources in a National Interest Priority Site located in Italy," *Energy & Environment*, vol. 27, no. 5, pp. 586–596, Aug. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0958305X16665536>.
- [6] M. A. Costagliola *et al.*, "Performances and emissions of a 4-stroke motorcycle fuelled with ethanol/gasoline blends," *Fuel*, vol. 183, pp. 470–477, Nov. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2016.06.105>.
- [7] P. Iodice, G. Langella, and A. Amoresano, "Ethanol in gasoline fuel blends: Effect on fuel consumption and engine out emissions of SI engines in cold operating conditions," *Applied Thermal Engineering*, vol. 130, pp. 1081–1089, Feb. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2017.11.090>.
- [8] A. Elgowainy, A. Burnham, M. Wang, J. Molburg, and A. Rousseau, "Well-To-Wheels Energy Use and Greenhouse Gas Emissions of Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicles," *SAE International Journal of Fuels and Lubricants*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 627–644, 2009.
- [9] M. Longo, W. Yaïci, and D. Zaninelli, "'Team Play' between Renewable Energy Sources and Vehicle Fleet to Decrease Air Pollution," *Sustainability*, vol. 8, no. 1, Jan. 2016, Art. no. 27, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su8010027>.
- [10] G. R. Chandra Mouli, P. Bauer, and M. Zeman, "System design for a solar powered electric vehicle charging station for workplaces," *Applied Energy*, vol. 168, pp. 434–443, Apr. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2016.01.110>.
- [11] A. K. Karmaker, Md. R. Ahmed, Md. A. Hossain, and Md. M. Sikder, "Feasibility assessment & design of hybrid renewable energy based electric vehicle charging station in Bangladesh," *Sustainable Cities and Society*, vol. 39, pp. 189–202, May 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2018.02.035>.
- [12] S. Khan, A. Ahmad, F. Ahmad, M. Shafaati Shemami, M. Saad Alam, and S. Khateeb, "A Comprehensive Review on Solar Powered Electric Vehicle Charging System," *Smart Science*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 54–79, Jan. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1080/23080477.2017.1419054>.
- [13] Y. Kassem, H. Gökçekuş, A. Irvanian, and R. Gökçekuş, "Predictive suitability of renewable energy for desalination plants: the case of güzelyurt region in northern Cyprus," *Modeling Earth Systems and Environment*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 3657–3677, Sep. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40808-021-01315-0>.
- [14] Y. Kassem, R. Al Zoubi, and H. Gökçekuş, "The Possibility of Generating Electricity Using Small-Scale Wind Turbines and Solar Photovoltaic Systems for Households in Northern Cyprus: A Comparative Study," *Environments*, vol. 6, no. 4, Apr. 2019, Art. no. 47, <https://doi.org/10.3390/environments6040047>.
- [15] Y. Kassem and H. Gökçekuş, "GHG Emissions and Energy Performance of 1MW Grid-Connected Solar PV Plant at Lefke in Northern Cyprus: A Case Study," *Disaster Science and Engineering*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 90–98, Dec. 2018.
- [16] Y. Kassem, H. Gökçekuş, and S. M. Alsayas, "Freestanding PV solar system- example of Lefke town in Northern Cyprus," *International Journal of Applied Engineering Research*, vol. 14, no. 11, pp. 2522–2526, 2019.
- [17] Y. Kassem, H. Gökçekuş, and A. Güvensoy, "Techno-Economic Feasibility of Grid-Connected Solar PV System at Near East University Hospital, Northern Cyprus," *Energies*, vol. 14, no. 22, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 7627, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14227627>.
- [18] Y. Kassem, H. Gökçekuş, and R. Gökçekuş, "Economic Feasibility of Large-Scale Renewable Energy Projects in Mountain Location, Northern Cyprus," in *Climate Change, Natural Resources and Sustainable Environmental Management*, 2022, pp. 66–71, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-04375-8_8.
- [19] Y. Kassem, H. Gökçekuş, and H. Çamur, "Economic assessment of renewable power generation based on wind speed and solar radiation in urban regions," *Global Journal of Environmental Science and Management*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 465–482, Oct. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.22034/gjesm.2018.04.007>.
- [20] C. Gamarra and J. J. Ronk, "Floating solar: an emerging opportunity at the energy-water nexus.," *Texas Water Journal*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 32–45, 2019.
- [21] Y. C. N. Duarte and P. C. Sentelhas, "NASA/POWER and DailyGridded weather datasets—how good they are for estimating maize yields in Brazil?," *International Journal of Biometeorology*, vol. 64, no. 3, pp. 319–329, Mar. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00484-019-01810-1>.
- [22] R. A. Escobar *et al.*, "Estimating the potential for solar energy utilization in Chile by satellite-derived data and ground station measurements," *Solar Energy*, vol. 121, pp. 139–151, Nov. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2015.08.034>.
- [23] Y. Kassem, H. Gökçekuş, and H. S. A. Lagili, "A Techno-Economic Viability Analysis of the Two-Axis Tracking Grid-Connected Photovoltaic Power System for 25 Selected Coastal Mediterranean Cities," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7508–7514, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4251>.
- [24] Y. Kassem, H. Çamur, and S. M. A. Alhuoti, "Solar Energy Technology for Northern Cyprus: Assessment, Statistical Analysis, and Feasibility Study," *Energies*, vol. 13, no. 4, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 940, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13040940>.
- [25] "NASA POWER | Prediction Of Worldwide Energy Resources." <https://power.larc.nasa.gov/>.
- [26] P. V. Minh, S. Le Quang, and M.-H. Pham, "Technical Economic Analysis of Photovoltaic-Powered Electric Vehicle Charging Stations under Different Solar Irradiation Conditions in Vietnam," *Sustainability*, vol. 13, no. 6, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 3528, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13063528>.
- [27] M. shafiei and A. Ghasemi-Marzbali, "Fast-charging station for electric vehicles, challenges and issues: A comprehensive review," *Journal of Energy Storage*, vol. 49, May 2022, Art. no. 104136, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2022.104136>.
- [28] Å. L. Sørensen, K. B. Lindberg, I. Sartori, and I. Andresen, "Analysis of residential EV energy flexibility potential based on real-world charging reports and smart meter data," *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 241, Jun. 2021, Art. no. 110923, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2021.110923>.
- [29] Y. Kassem, H. Gokcekus, O. A. M. Hamad, and F. M. B. Fayid, "Economic Viability of a 6.5kW Off-grid Solar PV with Various Sun-Tracking Systems in Northern Cyprus: A Case Study," *Engineering,*

- Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 10608–10621, Apr. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5744>.
- [30] H. A. Kazem and T. Khatib, "Techno-economical assessment of grid connected photovoltaic power systems productivity in Sohar, Oman," *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments*, vol. 3, pp. 61–65, Sep. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seta.2013.06.002>.
- [31] K. Mohammadi, M. Naderi, and M. Saghafifar, "Economic feasibility of developing grid-connected photovoltaic plants in the southern coast of Iran," *Energy*, vol. 156, pp. 17–31, Aug. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2018.05.065>.
- [32] "Energetech Solar: Pure sine wave inverter charger- for sustainability." <https://energetechsolar.com/off-grid-pure-sine-wave-inverters>.
- [33] "50KWh 48 Volt Module Energy Storage System | Energetech Solar." <https://energetechsolar.com/50kwh-48-volt-module-energy-storage-system>.
- [34] M. Obeng, S. Gyamfi, N. S. Derkyi, A. T. Kobo-bah, and F. Pephrah, "Technical and economic feasibility of a 50 MW grid-connected solar PV at UENR Nsoatre Campus," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 247, Feb. 2020, Art. no. 119159, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.119159>.
- [35] Y. Kassem, H. Gokcekus, I. A. A. Albakoush, and K. S. B. Abdullah, "Solar-Powered Solutions for the Water and Energy Shortage Problem: The Case Study of Nahr El Bared, Lebanon," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 10861–10869, Jun. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5858>.
- [36] Y. Kassem, H. Gokcekus, and F. A. R. Agila, "Techno-Economic Feasibility Assessment for the promotion of Grid-Connected Rooftop PV Systems in Botswana: A Case Study," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 10328–10337, Apr. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5668>.
- [37] A. B. Owolabi, B. E. K. Nsafon, J. W. Roh, D. Suh, and J.-S. Huh, "Validating the techno-economic and environmental sustainability of solar PV technology in Nigeria using RETScreen Experts to assess its viability," *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments*, vol. 36, Dec. 2019, Art. no. 100542, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seta.2019.100542>.
- [38] Y. Kassem and M. H. A. Abdalla, "Modeling predictive suitability to identify the potential of wind and solar energy as a driver of sustainable development in the Red Sea state, Sudan," *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, vol. 29, no. 29, pp. 44233–44254, Jun. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-022-19062-9>.

A Conceptual Digital Forensic Investigation Model Applicable to the Drone Forensics Field

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ABSTRACT

Although there is a considerable amount of studies in drone forensics that describe numerous practical and technical perspectives, there is a lack of a comprehensive investigation framework. This study used design science research methodology to design a conceptual model for the comprehensive investigation of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) under forensic conditions. This model can identify, capture, preserve, analyze, and document UAV incidents. The proposed model consists of four stages: preparation, data collection, analysis, and documentation. In the preparation stage, data are collected and analyzed about UAV-related resources, including the origin and model of the aircraft, any software or hardware installed onboard, and the legal framework and regulations in place. The data collection stage involves the completion of the collection process, where participants gather parts of the UAV and the data needed, such as the flight controller, flight log, and memory cards. The analysis stage involves analyzing the collected evidence. Lastly, the documentation stage involves documenting relevant evidence, analysis results, and any conclusions derived. This model provides a comprehensive process to forensically investigate UAV incidents and provides an efficient and effective approach to the analysis of UAV evidence, ensuring that evidence was collected and analyzed according to accepted forensic techniques. The proposed model can be applied to any UAV type and legal framework.

Keywords-drone forensics; digital forensics; design science research; unmanned aerial vehicles

I. INTRODUCTION

Digital forensics essentially focuses on capturing and analyzing cybercrimes and is divided into many subfields, such as database, Internet of Things (IoT), malware, network, drone, cloud, wireless, data, and mobile forensics [1]. These branches vary in terms of models, approaches, frameworks, policies, procedures, and activities. Therefore, digital forensics lacks a standardized framework that could unify these branches [2]. This field consists of two main stages, proactive and reactive forensics, both designed to resolve cybercrimes [3-4]. Proactive forensics refers to forensic readiness before a crime occurs. During this stage, digital evidence is collected to reduce future risks and disasters. On the other hand, reactive forensics focuses on the necessary procedures after the crime is committed. The primary objective of this stage is to locate, seize, preserve, analyze, and record cybercrime data.

Essentially, both stages are used in digital forensics, and the ISO/IEC 27043:2015 standard serves as the primary context for studies on proactive forensic approaches [5-14]. Drone forensics (DRF) aims to provide the tools and techniques necessary to identify and investigate potential drone-related incidents [15-17]. The primary focus of DRF is to identify the drone's owner, the activities that occurred during a drone-related incident, the nature of the data stored on the drone, and any evidence the drone may have left behind. A drone forensic process involves four steps. The drone must first be identified, which is performed using a combination of visual and electronic identification techniques. The drone must then be secured for forensic analysis. This involves stopping any moving parts, turning off the device, and taking precautions to avoid data manipulation [18-19]. Specialized software and hardware can be used to analyze drone data after they have been secured. Lastly, it is imperative to examine and document

the data gathered to determine if they contain any relevant evidence. In addition to data analysis, DRF researchers need a thorough understanding of the legal implications of drone use. Therefore, a solid understanding of drone laws and regulations and their consequences based on acquired evidence is fundamental. Investigating a drone incident is an essential task for law enforcement, government, and security personnel [20-23]. Through the integration of cutting-edge technology and in-depth legal knowledge, DRF can help investigators discover, investigate, and prosecute drone-related incidents.

This study used Design Science Research (DSR) methodology to design a conceptual forensic model for DRF. DSR was used in the construction of the representation component, and semantic analysis was applied to determine its structure and constituent elements. The proposed model consisted of four stages: preparation, collection, analysis, and documentation. In the preparation stage, it is necessary to determine the type of drone, define the investigation objective, and select the appropriate equipment. The collection stage involves collecting all the components related to the device, such as its controller, camera, etc. The subsequent analysis stage is used to identify the data sources and extract the necessary evidence. Finally, the necessary reports are compiled, documenting the evidence, the results of the analysis, and any conclusions derived. The proposed model can be used in any DRF investigation.

II. RELATED WORKS

Various models and frameworks have been proposed in DRF, based on the following four aspects: forensic, non-forensic, forensic framework, and forensic analysis applications [24-26]. In [8-9], the ways to ensure the best recovery of evidence related to drone incidents were discussed. Most studies emphasized the advantages of using Linux-based operating systems to collect information about the Linux filesystem. In [27], the Parrot A.R Drone 2.0 was used for digital forensic analysis, covering a variety of general data points and file types and using Google Earth to fully visualize the flight path. In [28], DRF was reviewed using DJI Phantom 2, initiating a detailed analysis of the hardware and software components of the drone and discussing their applicability to DRF. In [29], a specific tool was developed using Java-FX to efficiently visualize real-time flight control. Although this tool was not designed to work directly with forensics, it can build a strong integration between the controller and the drone, which could facilitate data transfer procedures and allow pilots to monitor sensor parameters such as IMU, GPS, and altitude. In [30], the DJI Phantom 2 Vision Plus was used to reconstruct the flight path of a UAV based on positional data. In [31], a preliminary forensic examination was described using Parrot AR Drone 2.0 and Parrot Bebop.

In [14], the main difficulties in UAV forensics were discussed before studying the UAV and flight controller individually. All flight-related data from the investigated device were retrieved in .pud file format, which was examined during the investigation process to extract a set of metadata such as the serial number of the UAV, the flight controller model, the flight controller application, and the date- and time-related flight data. Additionally, an identification stage was

followed to retrieve videos and images captured by the UAV onboard camera. Furthermore, the latitude/longitude coordinates of the locations of the captured images were preserved in the EXIF data. In this part, ownership can only be established when the UAV and controller are seized and the serial number of the device is identified. In [32], a non-forensic approach was integrated with data visualization using Parrot AR Drone 2.0. In [33], drone vulnerabilities and applications were investigated, along with their connections and cybersecurity-related problems. The results confirmed that there could be serious risks or consequences in circumstances where drones are hacked and misused by adversaries. In [34], a novel approach was proposed to comprehensively investigate UAVs using a 12-phase forensic framework. The suggested framework was experimentally validated on five commercial UAVs. Some of the components of each UAV tested were altered and some were added (if applicable). The major goal of these tests was to see if the framework applies to a thorough UAV analysis and if it covers all the different parts of any typical commercial UAV. The results showed that one major obstacle is the lack of law enforcement training procedures in UAVs. In [35], the DJI Phantom 3 standard was analyzed and the Drone Open Source Parser (DROP) tool was developed. The collected data were then classified into three groups: controller, drone, and phone/tablet. Finally, the .dat files generated by the UAV and the .txt files generated by the DJI GO application were examined. The files were encrypted first, then decoded, and flight information, including flight status, remote controls, Wi-Fi connections, motors, and GPS locations, was extracted. The collected data were analyzed and the DROP tool was used to examine the evidence files. In [36], the use of GPS coordinates was discussed as location evidence when investigating crimes committed using drones, extracting system logs, and using a third-party web-based platform to plot the flight path and visualize GPS coordinates on maps. In [37], a correlation investigation was performed on the flight data collected from the drone's SD card and mobile phone. The results showed that it was possible to establish a connection between the drone and the suspect to aid in a criminal investigation underway. In addition, by installing specialized software on personal UAV devices, a variety of digital artifacts can be obtained, such as GPS timestamps, videos, and images. In [38], the key log parameters of autonomous drones were examined and a comprehensive software architecture for DRFs was proposed, offering a user-friendly graphical user interface to extract and examine on-board flight data.

Several studies have used mobile forensic methods to extract data from drone mobile applications using open-source tools such as CSV View and ExifTool. In [39], forensic workstations running Windows and Kali Linux were used to perform the necessary forensic analyses on two drones, the DJI Phantom 3 and A.R Drone. The flight path data were primarily visualized using open-source tools like Geo-Player. This option requires a significant amount of data modification, as UAV systems lack a compatible built environment consisting of configuration tools, a package manager, and a compiler. In [40], the challenges associated with the forensic analysis of a UAV/drone were investigated. This study reviewed and analyzed the effectiveness of existing DRF guidelines and

provided a set of recommendations. The main drawback of UAV forensics is the lack of previously validated forensic sound tools. The next logical step would be to create various parsing tools that can analyze the original data and provide accurate and trustworthy information. UAVs should also be able to integrate radio communication services.

In [41], a framework was suggested to secure authentication and preserve privacy using id-based signcryption. RFID tags were used to track the drones and their temporary identity to maintain privacy. The average renewal of temporary identity was calculated using a simulation in which the speed and duration of the drones changed. In [42], a scenario was described in which security forces can use a shotgun or any other appropriate tool to bring down a suspected UAV. The study emphasized the necessity of identifying the software and hardware modules of the UAV before subjecting it to forensic investigation. The next step was to gather all available evidence, demonstrate the chain of custody, and examine the media or data loaded onto the device. The increasing illegal use of UAVs demonstrates a legal weakness in current aviation regulations. Therefore, there is a lack of knowledge and accepted practices regarding how to investigate UAV incidents. A comprehensive framework for drone forensic investigations was presented, taking into account both physical and digital forensics. A physical forensics model was created, capable of recognizing drone parts right at the crime scene. The framework proved to be effective enough to be implemented in post-flight analyses of the drone's performance. Furthermore, a powerful application was created to mainly concentrate on the analysis of critical log parameters using JavaFX 8.0. In [43], potential cyber-physical security risks were investigated to address any issues related to UAV security. This study provided a method to examine large-scale cyber-security attack vectors of such systems, based on four essential categories for UAV operations, and effective countermeasures to such attacks. In [44], software was developed to gain access to the sensors and logs inside the device under investigation, to estimate the effectiveness of using neutralization and strengthening processes.

In [45], the Distributed Agent-based Secure Mechanism (DASMIS) was proposed to monitor IoD and smart grid sensors using a hybrid peer-to-peer and client-server network architecture with little protocol overhead for fast and bandwidth-efficient communication. Each node in this system had a Python-based agent capable of scanning and detecting modifications, system calls, installed applications, and all currently running system programs, and burned-in read-only node IDs, IP, and MAC addresses. This mechanism also hashes and encrypts data, reports changes to the server located in the C&C center, and communicates with other peer nodes. The agent encrypts communication and securely authenticates and grants access between nodes, while attacks such as masquerading, modification, and denial of service are detected and prevented. In [46], a study was presented to help those responsible for data generation, analysis, validation, and/or optimization to recover trace evidence. In [47], the implementation of digital forensic analysis to enhance the Drone Forensic and Incident Response Plan (DFIR) was investigated. The results demonstrated that the Federal

Aviation Administration (FAA) can update the specifications of Unmanned Aerial Systems (UAS) based on two classifications. Furthermore, an in-depth literature review was conducted, concluding that there were limited studies related to incident responses and forensic analysis frameworks for remotely piloted aerial systems.

III. METHODOLOGY

This study designed a conceptual digital forensic model for UAVs based on DSR. This method produces unique and persistent objects for a specific problem space, which enables the exploration of analytics [48]. According to [49], the development process consists of two main stages: problem identification and the development stage, as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Developed approach.

A. Stage 1: Problem Identification

The existing literature was reviewed and relevant data were collected. This stage involved three major steps:

- Identifying search engines: Seven widely used search engines were used to gather data: Web of Science, Scopus, IEEE, Springer, Google Scholar, ACM, and Science Direct.
- Gathering drone forensics models: The keywords "Drones Forensics" and "Drone Forensics + Model" were used to gather data. This resulted in a total of 132 publications.
- Filtering data: The search was limited to publications between January 2000 and January 2021 from research journals, conferences, dissertations, and books, while all other document types were ignored. Table I shows the findings per search engine. This step left 25 articles that focused on DRF processes and technological perspectives, to be considered for further analysis.

TABLE I. FINDINGS FROM SEARCH-ENGINES

Database search engines	Number of DRF-related articles
Scopus	97
Web of Science	54
IEEE	15
Google Scholar	70
Springer	120
Science Direct	2
ACM	20

B. Stage 2: Development

This stage involved the development and validation of a drone forensic model. The steps involved in this stage were:

- Identification Process: This step identified the development and validation models as shown in Table II.
- Collection process: It is difficult to collect common concepts and processes from DRF models because it is a relatively new field and, consequently, the literature consists of only a limited number of such models. However, some general concepts and processes that could be extracted from these models included data collection, analysis and interpretation, legal and ethical considerations, data storage and preservation, digital evidence examination, and digital forensic examination. Additionally, some models may include specific concepts and processes such as drone surveillance, image analysis, and GPS tracking. The 25 identified models were used to extract common processes based on the extraction criteria outlined in [50].
- Combining extracted processes: Common processes with similar meanings or modes of operation were grouped into the same category. Each group shared similar ideas and procedures in their semantic or practical applications [57].

TABLE II. DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION MODELS

ID	Model Reference	Year
1	[29]	2015
2	[33]	2016
3	[28]	2016
4	[32]	2016
5	[36]	2017
6	[34]	2017
7	[35]	2017
8	[37]	2017
9	[39]	2017
10	[40]	2018
11	[41]	2018
12	[43]	2018
13	[44]	2018
14	[42]	2019
15	[45]	2019
16	[46]	2019
17	[47]	2019
18	[51]	2019
19	[52]	2019
20	[53]	2019
21	[54]	2020
22	[55]	2021
23	[18]	2022
24	[15]	2022
25	[56]	2023

- Developing process: The conceptual model presented in this step was based on the common processes proposed in the previous step. The proposed model consists of four investigation stages: preparation, collection, analysis, and documentation, as shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Conceptual digital forensics model for the DRF field.

1) Stage 1: Preparation

This stage aims at observing and securing the patterns of the drone flight path as well as capturing the complete streaming activities (e.g. photos, GPS data, and records). The monitoring component employs a firewall to filter incoming and outgoing wireless traffic for security reasons. The term filtering refers to the process of restricting access by looking at each packet's header information. Although certain laptops and mobile devices can counterfeit their identity to look like authorized network users, a firewall cannot catch all the misbehavior data. This stage involves four steps:

- Securing the area: The area around the suspected drone is secured by cordoning the area and notifying local authorities. It is important to ensure that all personnel entering the area wear protective clothing and gloves. Cordoning off the area can be done by installing a physical barrier or using warning signs to prevent unauthorized personnel or laypeople from entering. After the area has been sealed off, the incident should be reported to the local authorities so that appropriate measures could be taken to effectively secure the area. Additionally, local authorities can advise on how to safely dispose of any hazardous materials that may be present.

- Documenting the crime scene: Before accessing the drone, it must be ensured that there is a record of the incident in the form of photos and videos to provide a visual reference for the drone's location. Furthermore, any available evidence to support the claim that the drone had operated in that area must also be provided. To document a scene with a drone, the first step is to take pictures or videos of the area where the drone is stationed. Landmarks, buildings, or topographical characteristics relevant to the location of the drone should be included.
- Establishing the context of the incident: Drone types, suspects, and any pertinent information that can help in the investigation of the case should be analyzed. It is important to identify the type of drone used since drones of different manufacturers and models often have different capabilities, ranges, purposes, and applications. Additionally, the manufacturer and model of the drone could provide clues about the responsibility for the crime.
- Conducting a thorough examination of the crime scene: To facilitate the assessment of the event, it is crucial to conduct an extensive inspection of the crime scene to locate and gather any evidence that could facilitate the investigation. The first step in responding to a drone incident should be a thorough investigation of the site in question.

2) Stage 2: Data Collection

This is an important stage in any investigation, as it allows data to be collected and then analyzed to identify any indications of criminal activity. Data can be collected from the drone itself or external sources, such as telecommunication towers or cellular networks, depending on the type of drone. A drone may be equipped with onboard recording equipment, such as cameras, which can be analyzed for evidence of suspicious conduct. The collection process should be carried out following established procedures and protocols, regardless of the type of drone used, to ensure that any evidence acquired is admissible in court. The collection process may include obtaining a search warrant to gain access to the drone or its data. It might include downloading any records or data onboard, such as GPS coordinates, altitude, speed, and direction. In some circumstances, gathering data from a drone may require the assistance of other agencies or individuals to acquire access to the drone or its data. It is critical to maintain respect and diplomacy in such situations because it could be a sensitive topic for everyone involved. Finally, to obtain any evidence related to the suspected drone, the collection stage of a drone investigation is critical for investigators to stay up-to-date with the newest drone laws and procedures to ensure that any evidence acquired is legally admissible in court. This stage consists of three major steps:

- Capturing digital evidence: Obtaining digital data such as pictures, videos, and audio recordings from the drone's onboard cameras or other recording systems may be part of capturing digital evidence. Furthermore, metadata connected with the files saved on the drone's onboard storage device may be included in digital evidence. The onboard storage system may include a memory card, hard drive, or other types of digital storage medium. To gather

digital evidence from a drone, the drone must be seized and secured so that the digital evidence could be well protected. Once the drone has been secured, digital data can be recovered using forensic tools and techniques. Digital evidence should be extracted preserving their integrity and authenticity. Documenting the actions used to obtain the evidence is critical, as well as the environment in which it is obtained. Any tools used to extract evidence should also be examined and validated to ensure that the digital evidence is not corrupted or manipulated in any way. After extracting digital evidence, it should be analyzed to determine its relevance and accuracy. This could include inspecting the metadata associated with each file to discover where it came from and when it was generated or modified.

- Collecting physical evidence: To analyze a suspected drone, its outer shell or other components can be collected. Additionally, the drone's memory card or storage system must be properly removed and saved. Moreover, residue and other components left at the scene should be collected and preserved. Gathering evidence safely and effectively requires proper equipment and personnel.
- Capturing telemetry data: Flight logs, GPS locations, and other telemetry data may provide information on a drone's flight path. During an investigation involving drones, telemetry data must be collected to be delivered to law enforcement officers and other organizations that monitor and analyze drone activities.

3) Stage 3: Analysis

In this stage, patterns and trends are identified that can be applied to identify drone crimes, the locations they were committed, and the patterns associated with them. As part of this process, the data obtained are analyzed for possible links to potential crimes. These data include the types of drones used, locations, and other factors that could contribute to the crime. This stage involves four steps:

- Identifying data sources: An investigation cannot be successful without identifying the data sources, which is the first step in analyzing and interpreting the data. When identifying data sources, several factors should be considered. It is important to first determine what type of data was acquired to identify the data sources. A drone's movement, altitude, payload, or anything else useful could be included in this data category. Considering the data source can also provide insight into the dependability and accuracy of the data.
- Examining the data: Data must be thoroughly checked for any trends or anomalies that could indicate the presence of drones. First, it should be determined where the data came from. There is a necessity to differentiate between data collected from common or private resources, for example, data gained from surveillance or safety cameras.
- Reconstructing the timeline: To establish a timeline, it is vital to take great care of all alleged drone actions. If an investigator can identify the way the drone worked in the past, then it may be possible to rebuild a timeline of its actions in the future. All available data should be used to

recreate the timeline using all available information. Among the drone data that can be collected are altitude, speed, and GPS coordinates. Recording a drone flight, in addition to providing video and audio, can provide additional clarity to the sequence of events. Drone debris, observations, and eyewitnesses can also contribute to the gathering of more information. To construct the timeline, all data need to be collected first. Data points need to be arranged in the right sequence to be able to develop the timeline. To compare the data with the timeframe, it is necessary to examine the data over time. Based on information such as the time the drone took off and landed, investigators can use that information to create a timeline for the investigation. The investigator can also check for inconsistencies in the timeline. If data points contradict each other, the investigator can look for additional evidence that favors one over the other and, therefore, can be used to rebuild and verify the timeline. Understanding what occurred during a suspected drone operation necessitates reconstructing the timeline of the drone's operations, which assists the investigator in gaining knowledge of the sequence of events that occurred by collecting important data points and piecing them together in the correct order.

- Determining the prevalence of drone crime: Drone crimes can be analyzed for types, trends, and potential solutions to reduce or eradicate them. This can be done by analyzing the data collected. As a starting point, it is vital to recognize that many types of drone crimes are increasingly occurring across the globe.

4) Stage 4: Documentation

Each stage of the drone investigation should be recognized properly. This stage covers various actions such as classifying the drone, its worker, and its site, conducting meetings with the worker, and assembling photos, videos, and other available evidence. Additionally, any results during the examination must be recognized, such as laws or principles, consequences delivered, or other consequences arising. A detailed examination description will be given lastly based on this documentation, which will guide future investigations. This stage includes several steps: generating reports and presenting the evidence.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

UAVs can serve a variety of different purposes, including surveillance, inspection, data collection, and delivery. A growing number of these devices are used by individuals for malicious purposes, which requires the development of robust forensic frameworks to investigate and manage them. This study developed a forensic framework for drones and UAVs. At first, the history and existing forensic work on UAVs was discussed. In addition, this study discussed the current obstacles and problems associated with the use of drones and UAVs in the field of investigative research. The lack of standardization and the complexity of the hardware and software components of UAVs and drones, which are associated with their application in forensics, were also examined.

The proposed model consists of four main stages: preparation, collection, analysis, and documentation. During the preparation stage, the investigation requirements are identified, the necessary equipment is collected, and key personnel who can assist with the investigation are employed. This collection stage is an essential part of the process to obtain all crucial information on the drone and any external systems that may be involved. Furthermore, it involves the establishment of essential safety protocols that protect the safety of all staff and minimize the risk of poisoning evidence. During this stage, the drone and any components associated with it are physically obtained. The drone and its components should be secured to prevent contamination or destruction of any evidence. After analyzing the evidence, a determination is made as to whether criminal activity has occurred. To accomplish this, the drone and any components connected to it must be inspected for potential signs of criminal activity. It might be necessary to examine the flight logs of the drone and/or analyze photographs and videos that the drone has taken. The documentation stage is the last step in the investigation process, during which all evidence and information related to the investigation is recorded. At this stage, it is important to document the results of the analysis and any other information that may be valuable for future inquiries. This information should be stored in a secure and tamperproof manner to be used as evidence in a criminal case if necessary. The proposed DRF model is a consistent approach to investigating drone-related crimes. It is possible to verify that the evidence was acquired and examined appropriately if the investigators follow this model and adhere to it. A successful criminal prosecution depends on secure and documented evidence, which is one of the most important factors. Additionally, this framework can help investigators ensure that any criminal activity involving drones is thoroughly investigated and prosecuted.

V. CONCLUSION

UAVs play a critical role in forensic investigations. In this paper, a four-stage forensic investigation model was presented, which can be used to recognize, assemble, examine, and document incidents involving drones. Based on this model, law enforcement agencies will be able to improve their examination procedures for such crimes. Future work must explore the efficacy of the suggested model in a real-world setting. Additionally, further research should be carried out to investigate the potential of UAVs to be used in a broader range of forensic applications. Finally, this model should be subjected to further research due to its potential to be tailored to meet the demands of law enforcement agencies.

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REFERENCES

- [1] V. R. KEBANDE and I. Ray, "A Generic Digital Forensic Investigation Framework for Internet of Things (IoT)," in *2016 IEEE 4th International*

- Conference on Future Internet of Things and Cloud (FiCloud), Vienna, Austria, Dec. 2016, pp. 356–362, <https://doi.org/10.1109/FiCloud.2016.57>.
- [2] V. R. Kebande, "Industrial internet of things (IIoT) forensics: The forgotten concept in the race towards industry 4.0," *Forensic Science International: Reports*, vol. 5, Jul. 2022, Art. no. 100257, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fsir.2022.100257>.
- [3] S. M. Makura, H. S. Venter, R. A. Ikuesan, V. R. Kebande, and N. M. Karie, "Proactive Forensics: Keystroke Logging from the Cloud as Potential Digital Evidence for Forensic Readiness Purposes," in *2020 IEEE International Conference on Informatics, IoT, and Enabling Technologies (ICIoT)*, Doha, Qatar, Oct. 2020, pp. 200–205, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIoT48696.2020.9089494>.
- [4] V. R. Kebande and H. S. Venter, "Requirements for Achieving Digital Forensic Readiness in the Cloud Environment using an NMB Solution," presented at the 11th International Conference on Cyber Warfare and Security ICCWS, Boston, MA, USA, Mar. 2016.
- [5] V. R. Kebande, N. M. Karie, R. A. Ikuesan, and H. S. Venter, "Ontology-driven perspective of CFRaaS," *WIREs Forensic Science*, vol. 2, no. 5, 2020, Art. no. e1372, <https://doi.org/10.1002/wfs2.1372>.
- [6] V. R. Kebande and H. S. Venter, "A comparative analysis of digital forensic readiness models using CFRaaS as a baseline," *WIREs Forensic Science*, vol. 1, no. 6, 2019, Art. no. e1350, <https://doi.org/10.1002/wfs2.1350>.
- [7] A. Valjarevic and H. S. Venter, "Harmonised digital forensic investigation process model," in *2012 Information Security for South Africa*, Johannesburg, South Africa, Dec. 2012, pp. 1–10, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISSA.2012.6320441>.
- [8] V. R. Kebande, N. M. Karie, and H. S. Venter, "Adding digital forensic readiness as a security component to the IoT domain," *International Journal on Advanced Science Engineering Information Technology*, vol. 8, no. 1, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.18517/ijaseit.8.1.2115>.
- [9] H. Munkhondya, A. Ikuesan, and H. Venter, "Digital Forensic Readiness Approach for Potential Evidence Preservation in Software-Defined Networks," in *Proceedings of the 14th International Conference on Cyber Warfare and Security*, Stellenbosch, South Africa, Feb. 2019, pp. 268–276.
- [10] A. R. Ikuesan, S. Abd Razak, M. Salleh, and H. S. Venter, "Leveraging Human Thinking Style for User Attribution in Digital Forensic Process," *International Journal on Advanced Science, Engineering and Information Technology*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 198–206, 2017.
- [11] A. Singh, A. R. Ikuesan, and H. S. Venter, "Digital Forensic Readiness Framework for Ransomware Investigation," in *Digital Forensics and Cyber Crime*, New Orleans, LA, USA, 2019, pp. 91–105, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-05487-8_5.
- [12] S. Makura, H. S. Venter, V. R. Kebande, N. M. Karie, R. A. Ikuesan, and S. Alawadi, "Digital forensic readiness in operational cloud leveraging ISO/IEC 27043 guidelines on security monitoring," *Security and Privacy*, vol. 4, no. 3, 2021, Art. no. e149, <https://doi.org/10.1002/spy2.149>.
- [13] V. R. Kebande, N. M. Karie, K.-K. R. Choo, and S. Alawadi, "Digital forensic readiness intelligence crime repository," *Security and Privacy*, vol. 4, no. 3, 2021, Art. no. e151, <https://doi.org/10.1002/spy2.151>.
- [14] A. Ali, S. A. Razak, S. H. Othman, and A. Mohammed, "Extraction of Common Concepts for the Mobile Forensics Domain," in *Recent Trends in Information and Communication Technology*, 2018, pp. 141–154, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-59427-9_16.
- [15] F. M. Alotaibi, A. Al-Dhaqm, and Y. D. Al-Otaibi, "A Novel Forensic Readiness Framework Applicable to the Drone Forensics Field," *Computational Intelligence and Neuroscience*, vol. 2022, Feb. 2022, Art. no. e8002963, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/8002963>.
- [16] S. O. Baror, H. S. Venter, and V. R. Kebande, "Conceptual Model for Crowd-Sourcing Digital Forensic Evidence," in *Innovations in Smart Cities Applications Volume 5*, 2022, pp. 1085–1099, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-94191-8_88.
- [17] T. Hungwe, Hein. S. Venter, and V. R. Kebande, "Scenario-Based Digital Forensic Investigation of Compromised MySQL Database," in *2019 IST-Africa Week Conference (IST-Africa)*, Nairobi, Kenya, Feb. 2019, pp. 1–11, <https://doi.org/10.23919/ISTAfrICA.2019.8764819>.
- [18] A. A. Alhussan, A. Al-Dhaqm, W. M. S. Yafooz, S. B. A. Razak, A.-H. M. Emara, and D. S. Khafaga, "Towards Development of a High Abstract Model for Drone Forensic Domain," *Electronics*, vol. 11, no. 8, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 1168, <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics11081168>.
- [19] V. R. Kebande and H. S. Venter, "CFRaaS: architectural design of a Cloud Forensic Readiness as-a-Service Model using NMB solution as a forensic agent," *African Journal of Science, Technology, Innovation and Development*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 749–769, Oct. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1080/20421338.2019.1585675>.
- [20] F. M. Alotaibi, A. Al-Dhaqm, Y. D. Al-Otaibi, and A. A. Alsewari, "A Comprehensive Collection and Analysis Model for the Drone Forensics Field," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 17, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 6486, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22176486>.
- [21] V. R. Kebande and R. A. Ikuesan, "Virtual sensor forensics," in *Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference on Intelligent and Innovative Computing Applications*, Jun. 2020, pp. 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3415088.3415117>.
- [22] V. R. Kebande, H. S. Ntsamo, and H. S. Venter, "Towards a prototype for Achieving Digital Forensic Readiness in the Cloud using a Distributed NMB Solution," presented at the 15th European Conference on Cyber Warfare and Security, Munich, Germany, 2016.
- [23] A. Ali *et al.*, "Financial Fraud Detection Based on Machine Learning: A Systematic Literature Review," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 12, no. 19, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 9637, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12199637>.
- [24] N. M. Karie and V. R. Kebande, "Knowledge Management as a Strategic Asset in Digital Forensic Investigations," *International Journal of Cyber-Security and Digital Forensics*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 10–21, Jan. 2018.
- [25] A. Al-Dhaqm, R. A. Ikuesan, V. R. Kebande, S. Razak, and F. M. Ghabban, "Research Challenges and Opportunities in Drone Forensics Models," *Electronics*, vol. 10, no. 13, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 1519, <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics10131519>.
- [26] S. O. Baror, H. S. Venter, and V. R. Kebande, "A Framework for Concurrent Contact-Tracing and Digital Evidence Analysis in Heterogeneous Environments," in *Innovations in Smart Cities Applications Volume 4*, 2021, pp. 1183–1196, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-66840-2_90.
- [27] H. Bouafif, F. Kamoun, F. Iqbal, and A. Marrington, "Drone Forensics: Challenges and New Insights," in *2018 9th IFIP International Conference on New Technologies, Mobility and Security (NTMS)*, Paris, France, Oct. 2018, pp. 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1109/NTMS.2018.8328747>.
- [28] David Kovar, Greg Dominguez, and Cindy Murphy, "UAV (aka drone) Forensics," presented at the SANS DFIR Summit, Austin, TX, USA, Jun. 2016.
- [29] V. Mhatre, S. Chavan, A. Samuel, A. Patil, A. Chittimilla, and N. Kumar, "Embedded video processing and data acquisition for unmanned aerial vehicle," in *2015 International Conference on Computers, Communications, and Systems (ICCCS)*, Kanyakumari, India, Aug. 2015, pp. 141–145, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CCOMS.2015.7562889>.
- [30] A. Roder, K.-K. R. Choo, and N.-A. Le-Khac, "Unmanned Aerial Vehicle Forensic Investigation Process: Dji Phantom 3 Drone As A Case Study," arXiv, Apr. 23, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1804.08649>.
- [31] G. Horsman, "Unmanned aerial vehicles: A preliminary analysis of forensic challenges," *Digital Investigation*, vol. 16, pp. 1–11, Mar. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.diin.2015.11.002>.
- [32] T. Procházka, "Capturing, Visualizing, and Analyzing Data from Drones," BSc Thesis, Charles University, Prague, Czech Republic, 2016.
- [33] M. Mohan, "Cybersecurity in drones," MSc Thesis, Utica College, New York, NY, USA, 2016.
- [34] U. Jain, M. Rogers, and E. T. Matson, "Drone forensic framework: Sensor and data identification and verification," in *2017 IEEE Sensors Applications Symposium (SAS)*, Glassboro, NJ, USA, Mar. 2017, pp. 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1109/SAS.2017.7894059>.

- [35] D. R. Clark, C. Meffert, I. Baggili, and F. Breiting, "DROP (DRone Open source Parser) your drone: Forensic analysis of the DJI Phantom III," *Digital Investigation*, vol. 22, pp. S3–S14, Aug. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.diin.2017.06.013>.
- [36] S. E. Prastya, I. Riadi, and A. Luthfi, "Forensic Analysis of Unmanned Aerial Vehicle to Obtain GPS Log Data as Digital Evidence," *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security*, vol. 15, no. 3, pp. 280–285, Mar. 2017.
- [37] M. Llewellyn, "DJI Phantom 3 – Drone Forensic data exploration.," Edith Cowan University, Perth, Australia, 2017.
- [38] A. L. P. S. Renduchintala, A. Albehadili, and A. Y. Javaid, "Drone Forensics: Digital Flight Log Examination Framework for Micro Drones," in *2017 International Conference on Computational Science and Computational Intelligence (CSCI)*, Las Vegas, NV, USA, Sep. 2017, pp. 91–96, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CSCI.2017.15>.
- [39] T. E. A. Barton and M. A. Hannan Bin Azhar, "Forensic analysis of popular UAV systems.," in *2017 Seventh International Conference on Emerging Security Technologies (EST)*, Canterbury, UK, Sep. 2017, pp. 91–96, <https://doi.org/10.1109/EST.2017.8090405>.
- [40] R. L. Fairbrother, "A project completed as part of the requirements for the BSc (Hons) Computer Forensics and Security," University of Derby, Derby, UK, 2018.
- [41] S. Benzarti, B. Triki, and O. Korbaa, "Privacy Preservation and Drone Authentication Using ID-Based Signcryption," in *New Trends in Intelligent Software Methodologies, Tools and Techniques - Proceedings of the 17th International Conference SoMeT*, 2018, pp. 226–239, <https://doi.org/10.3233/978-1-61499-900-3-226>.
- [42] A. Renduchintala, F. Jahan, R. Khanna, and A. Y. Javaid, "A comprehensive micro unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV/Drone) forensic framework," *Digital Investigation*, vol. 30, pp. 52–72, Sep. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.diin.2019.07.002>.
- [43] E. S. Dawam, X. Feng, and D. Li, "Autonomous Aerial Vehicles in Smart Cities: Potential Cyber-Physical Threats," in *2018 IEEE 20th International Conference on High Performance Computing and Communications*, Exeter, UK, Jun. 2018, pp. 1497–1505, <https://doi.org/10.1109/HPCC/SmartCity/DSS.2018.00247>.
- [44] J. L. Esteves, E. Cottais, and C. Kasmi, "Unlocking the Access to the Effects Induced by IEMI on a Civilian UAV," in *2018 International Symposium on Electromagnetic Compatibility (EMC EUROPE)*, Amsterdam, Netherlands, Dec. 2018, pp. 48–52, <https://doi.org/10.1109/EMCEurope.2018.8484990>.
- [45] A. Fitwi, Y. Chen, and N. Zhou, "An agent-administrator-based security mechanism for distributed sensors and drones for smart grid monitoring," in *Signal Processing, Sensor/Information Fusion, and Target Recognition XXVIII*, May 2019, vol. 11018, pp. 173–188, <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2519006>.
- [46] Z. V. Jones, C. Gwinnett, and A. R. W. Jackson, "The effect of tape type, taping method and tape storage temperature on the retrieval rate of fibres from various surfaces: An example of data generation and analysis to facilitate trace evidence recovery validation and optimisation," *Science & Justice*, vol. 59, no. 3, pp. 268–291, May 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scijus.2018.12.003>.
- [47] F. E. Salamh, U. Karabiyik, M. Rogers, and F. Al-Hazemi, "Drone Disrupted Denial of Service Attack (3DOS): Towards an Incident Response and Forensic Analysis of Remotely Piloted Aerial Systems (RPASs)," in *2019 15th International Wireless Communications & Mobile Computing Conference (IWCMC)*, Tangier, Morocco, Jun. 2019, pp. 704–710, <https://doi.org/10.1109/IWCMC.2019.8766538>.
- [48] S. T. March and G. F. Smith, "Design and natural science research on information technology," *Decision Support Systems*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 251–266, Dec. 1995, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-9236\(94\)00041-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-9236(94)00041-2).
- [49] A. Al-dhaqm, S. Razak, S. H. Othman, A. Ngadi, M. N. Ahmed, and A. A. Mohammed, "Development and validation of a Database Forensic Metamodel (DBFM)," *PLOS ONE*, vol. 12, no. 2, 2017, Art. no. e0170793, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0170793>.
- [50] A. Al-Dhaqm *et al.*, "CDBFIP: Common Database Forensic Investigation Processes for Internet of Things," *IEEE Access*, vol. 5, pp. 24401–24416, 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2017.2762693>.
- [51] N. Mei, "An Approach to Unmanned Aircraft Systems Forensics Framework," Ph.D. dissertation, Capitol Technology University, South Laurel, MD, USA, 2019.
- [52] F. Le Roy, C. Roland, D. Le Jeune, and J.-P. Diguët, "Risk assessment of SDR-based attacks with UAVs," in *2019 16th International Symposium on Wireless Communication Systems (ISWCS)*, Oulu, Finland, Dec. 2019, pp. 222–226, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISWCS.2019.8877144>.
- [53] S. Sciancalepore, O. A. Ibrahim, G. Oligeri, and R. Di Pietro, "Detecting Drones Status via Encrypted Traffic Analysis," in *Proceedings of the ACM Workshop on Wireless Security and Machine Learning*, Feb. 2019, pp. 67–72, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3324921.3328791>.
- [54] F. Lakew Yihunie, A. K. Singh, and S. Bhatia, "Assessing and Exploiting Security Vulnerabilities of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles," in *Smart Systems and IoT: Innovations in Computing*, Singapore, 2020, pp. 701–710, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-8406-6_66.
- [55] C. C. Yang, H. Chuang, and D. Y. Kao, "Drone Forensic Analysis Using Relational Flight Data: A Case Study of DJI Spark and Mavic Air," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 192, pp. 1359–1368, Jan. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2021.08.139>.
- [56] S. Silalahi, T. Ahmad, and H. Studiawan, "Transformer-Based Named Entity Recognition on Drone Flight Logs to Support Forensic Investigation," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 3257–3274, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3234605>.
- [57] A. Al-Dhaqm, S. A. Razak, K. Siddique, R. A. Ikuesan, and V. R. Kebande, "Towards the Development of an Integrated Incident Response Model for Database Forensic Investigation Field," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 145018–145032, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3008696>.

Investigating the Effect on Productivity of a Geospatial Ticket Management System for Power Distribution Network Studies

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ABSTRACT

Increasing productivity without jeopardizing the network's operation, consumers' experience, and the safety and integrity of procedures, is a major goal for all utilities. Scheduling of work has a direct impact on productivity, especially in the case of utilities that cover a wide geographical area using a limited number of employees. In the case of power utilities, however, scheduling has to consider, apart from the location of issues, the type and technical characteristics of each issue as well as its priority has to be considered in order to produce an optimum schedule. This paper focuses on the impact on productivity of a geospatial ticket management system considering the experience from such a system applied on network studies performed by HEDNO, the Greek Distribution Network Operator, in Patras Area. The term "network studies" is used to describe the study of all expansion and alteration works, ranging from a single Low Voltage (LV) pole installation to major Medium Voltage (MV) network rearrangements/expansion, and includes visits and measurements on the actual location as well as in-door calculations. In Patras Area, the local HEDNO division implemented in 2021-2022 a geospatial ticket managing system, based on available network data and custom Google Maps, aiming to increase its productivity by optimizing the scheduling process. Initial results published in February 2022, showed a significant productivity increase (up to 42%). However, the initial results considered a time span of only one month and thus could easily be misleading. This paper revisits the issue considering a larger time span (more than two years) that should provide more trustworthy results. It also briefly presents the latest updates and improvements made to the system. Results show that the increase in the number of studies and their predicted costs are similar to the initial results, with the increase in productivity being around 41%. In September 2022, HEDNO set the very ambitious goal of significantly increasing the overall production of network studies (more than double in terms of predicted costs) and the use of such a system can provide valuable help towards achieving this goal.

Keywords-power distribution network; ticket management system; geospatial; georeference; productivity;

I. INTRODUCTION

Increasing productivity is a major concern for all organizations and businesses worldwide. However, an exact definition of the term or an algorithm to measure its increase or decrease is not easy to be provided as there are many factors and metrics that can be considered [1-3]. In the power sector, measuring overall productivity is a well-established field that considers many factors [4-6]. However, in the context of this paper, the term is used to describe simply the volume of produced work considering both the number of completed works and their predicted costs. The case study is the Network Engineering & Construction Section (NECS) of HEDNO's Patras Area, Greece (HEDNO being the Greek Electricity Distribution Network Operator). In 2021, NECS decided to adopt a geospatial ticket management system to increase its productivity through improved scheduling [7]. Initial results

published in February 2022 showed a significant increase in productivity ranging from 10% to 42% depending on the values considered each time [7]. However, a time span of only one month was considered as [7] focused mainly on presenting the system and initial one-month results were provided as an indication of potential improvement that the system could provide. It should be noted that, as explained in [7], this system was applied on both studies and actual construction works. Considering however that construction works are performed by outside contractors which are allowed to produce and follow their own schedule, in order to safely assess the impact of the system the current paper focuses on the results related to network studies as these were performed by HEDNO personnel only.

To assess the productivity of the network studies subsection one must consider both the number of conducted studies and the accumulated predicted costs, as neither one of these values,

when considered alone, can be fully representative of the actual workload and the productivity of the workforce. This is because simpler and smaller studies that can be conducted in less time generally result to lower predicted costs. On the other hand, larger and more complicated studies usually demand more time and result in rather higher predicted costs. This is especially the case when a study is related to underground lines [8-10]. Thus, if a large increase is documented in the number of studies but not in the accumulated predicted cost, this could be a hint that a bulk volume of simpler studies was conducted. On the other hand, if an increase is recorded in predicted costs but not in the actual number of studies, then this may be an indication that the same man-hours were reallocated from simpler studies to complicated studies or studies related to underground works.

In the context of a power distribution utility, especially one operating as HEDNO does in Greece, it is essential to note that neither aspect (number of studies and predicted costs) can be neglected. Further, the importance and priority of each task is not related to the complexity and cost of the related study. Factors such as safety and Guaranteed Services to Consumers [11] are the ones primarily to be considered. It has now been more than two years since the system has been incorporated in NECS's everyday work and the current manuscript aims to provide a report on the actual effect of this system on productivity considering both the number of studies and their accumulated predicted cost. It is important to note that there has not been any significant change related to other factors that could affect these values so it would be safe to attribute the changes to the use of the considered system.

II. SET-UP

A. Initial Set-up

The geographical area and considered network is presented in detail in [7]. The area covers over 1,500 km² and more than 200,000 consumers connected to over 3,000 MV/LV transformers. The basic characteristics of the geospatial ticketing system and several screenshots can also be found in [7]. The initial form of the ticketing system was developed following the following principles [7]:

- The system's main initial goal was to digitize and provide a geospatial representation of issues documented during the network's yearly inspection.
- Custom made Google Maps were used as a geospatial ticketing tool following some simple rules.
- A Point-Of-Interest (POI) was created in the position of each MV/LV transformer and indicated with the use of a small dot icon.
- Each LV ticket was attributed to the POI of the MV/LV transformer that fed the considered LV circuit, thus making this POI "active".
- Each MV ticket was attributed to a single POI, even if it was referred to a large line segment. The POI was to be placed roughly in the position of the issue.
- An active POI was to be indicated with icons (circles) of different color according to the priority of the issue described in the active ticket (low or high). The letters XT or MT were placed inside each icon to indicate LV or MV respectively.
- Multiple LV tickets could be attributed to the same LV POI. If the LV POI had an active high priority ticket, its icon would correspond to that ticket regardless of the number of low priority tickets that could also have been attributed to that particular LV POI.
- When a study was assigned, the corresponded POI icon's color was changed accordingly, and a small wrench sketch was also added to the icon.
- When there were no active tickets attributed to a POI, the POI was labelled "inactive" and this was indicated by a specific icon: a small dot for an inactive LV POI and a smaller (compared to active POI icons) green circle with the letters MT for an inactive MV POI.

A detailed table with all POI icons for the initial set-up can be found in [7]. Through everyday use, minor adjustments and updates were conducted, mainly related to the presentation of POIs. The basic changes are discussed in the next section.

B. New Set-up

The initial scheme made no distinction between different type of LV tickets. This however meant that the user had to click on each LV POI to get a view of the ticket type, which was highly impractical. Thus, it was decided to create different icons for the basic different categories of issues usually described in tickets, as shown in Table I. The color and size of these POI icons vary to provide a visual aid related to the priority and importance of each category. In the new set-up, it was decided to include additional POIs and icons for consumer issues that could either be related to their connection to the network (connecting a new consumer or modifying an already active connection) or to construction works that create clearance issues. As explained in [7], according to Greek law the distribution network operator is allowed to construct and install network installations in private and public properties and no expropriation or easement is applied on the properties. Thus, property owners are still allowed to build on their property and the operator is expected to move the network accordingly in order to ensure clearance. This often creates a situation where a study is put on hold until detailed information is provided by the consumer and considered by the operator. Similar conditions apply for consumer connection issues as such studies may also be put on hold for a variety of reasons. Further, the operator is expected to expand the network accordingly when asked by local authorities, in order to provide poles that can support lights for public roads and areas. In that case, a rough initial study is performed on site in order to calculate the number of poles and the possible need of expanding the MV network. Then, the calculated cost is reported to local authorities which may choose to pay it or not (or even ask for a modified study). After the payment is made, a final detailed study has to be conducted.

Different icons have been created to depict all these different cases as shown in Table II. All these extra POIs are placed in the actual location of the issue for ease, and when the corresponding study is completed, the extra POIs are deleted, and the description and serial number of the issue/study is included in the attributes of the POI of the MV/LV transformer that feeds the considered circuit. A screenshot of the system is shown in Figure 1. Another improvement was adding additional information/attributes in POIs. As shown in Figure 2, POI attributes now include some additional boxes that are

used by users to write comments, information on previously cancelled or completed tickets, instructions etc. The approach of the initial system was that information regarding tickets would be depicted and then removed when the ticket was resolved. It soon became evident that these information should remain in the system in order to be visible and searchable at any time. This way, the user is able to identify duplicate issues or studies, a major factor that reduces productivity [7]. An instructions text was also added in each POI in order to help users being consistent when typing data.

Fig. 1. A view of the Patras area study map with all POIs (screenshot from Google Maps, Map Data (c) 2023 TerraMetrics). The screenshot was taken shortly after the tickets from the 2023 yearly inspection had been received, which explains the large number of depicted POIs.

TABLE I. ACTIVE LV POI ICONS

	Transformer should be moved to a new location		Clearance issue
	Distribution box damaged and needs to be replaced		Conductors to be replaced by wire
	Distribution box needs to be replaced with a larger one		Transformer needs an additional crossarm
	Part of the network needs to be removed		Assigned
	Pole(s) needs to be replaced		Low priority (not specific)
	Tilted pole or guy-wire issue		High priority (not specific)

TABLE II. CONSUMER RELATED LV POI ICONS

	Consumer connection (new request)		Consumer connection (study assigned)
			Consumer connection (additional action required by consumer)
	Network should be moved due to construction works (new request)		Network should be moved due to construction works (study assigned)
			Network should be moved due to construction works (additional action required by consumer)
	Network expansion for public light (new request)		Network expansion for public light (initial study conducted and pending payment)
			Network expansion for public light (payment done, study pending)

III. RESULTS

The yearly work production of the network study subsection for the past three years is shown in Table III. The increase is separately depicted in Table IV. It should be noted that exporting the correct values from the archives is not an easy task as there is not a single software, universally used to track all issues. Instead, HEDNO uses a variety of software to track different works (e.g. RES related and not RES related studies) or to track different aspects of the same work (e.g. one software to track the dates related to a customer-related issue and another to track the payment and yet another to track metering issues etc). A brief list of software used around the time of HEDNO's separation from PPC can be found in [12] but the list has significantly increased since. Thus, a significant amount of workhours is actually necessary in order to acquire trustworthy data related to productivity.

Fig. 2. The revised attributes box of POIs.

An easy way to bypass this problem is to consider the archives of the construction subsector within NECS [7]. These archives include the studies that are actually forwarded for construction each month and thus may exhibit some time-delay between the date of the study and the date that the study was forwarded for construction, but since all studies are forwarded for construction with a somewhat steady pace, this deviation can be considered negligible when trying to assess the overall trend. It should also be noted that all contracts between HEDNO and outside contractors consider the labor cost for each work and not the mixed cost, as most materials are provided by HEDNO. This also helps to better assess the productivity of the network studies subsection as it removes the cost of materials which would inflate the accumulated costs.

TABLE III. PRODUCTIVITY PER YEAR

Year	Number of studies	Predicted labor cost (mil. €)
2020	1308	2.15
2021	1471	2.9
2022	1842	3.04

TABLE IV. PRODUCTIVITY INCREASE

Time-span	Increase of number of studies	Increase of predicted labor cost (mil. €)
2020-2021	163 (12.46%)	0.75 (34.88%)
2021-2022	371 (25.22%)	0.14 (4.82%)
2020-2022	534 (40.82%)	0.89 (41.39%)

IV. DISCUSSION

Considering the data shown in Tables III and IV it is easy to observe that in the first year of application (2021) the increase was more evident on the predicted labor costs (34.88%) and not so much on the number of studies (12.46%).

This hints that larger and more difficult studies may have been conducted. However, as the system was fully incorporated in the second year, the increase was more evident on the number of studies (25.22%) and not so much on the predicted labor costs (4.82%). This hints that by fully utilizing the system and acquiring a wide view of the issues to be studied, it gradually became possible to schedule routes for the personnel that included a larger number of issues even though the related costs per issue were lower. As such issues (scattered and of low cost) are usually safety-related, this also hints that a major improvement in network's safety has been achieved. However, these results also show that there is a limit to the productivity increase that can be achieved by optimizing the personnel's schedule, and it is rather possible that this limit has been reached.

Overall, it is shown that the incorporation of the system has significantly increased productivity over these two years regardless of the value considered. As mentioned earlier, it is not easy to pin down and clearly define productivity, but the fact that both of the considered values are that similar is a strong indication that the produced workload has been increased by such a factor. Since no other factor has significantly changed over these two years, it is safe to assume that the incorporation of the geospatial ticket management system is largely (if not only) responsible for this increase.

It should be noted that in September 2022, HEDNO signed a new contract with construction contractors that significantly modified the terms (for a brief description of changes see [16]). A significant change was that vegetation management works, would now be included in the works studied and monitored by NECS (whereas it was previously studied and monitored by the Network Operation & Maintenance Section (NOMS) [7]). However, this change was mostly logistic as the actual studies were largely still conducted by NOMS personnel. However, these studies were now included in the sum of studies monitored by NECS and so had to manually removed from the dataset considered in this paper, in order for the data of 2022 to be equivalent to those of 2021. Further, the new contract demanded that the monthly predicted labor cost of studies assigned to the contractor had to be increased by a factor larger than two. This increase could not be achieved simply by vegetation management works. As discussed earlier, the productivity increase achieved through the use of the geospatial management system seems to have reached its limit, so NECS is expected to add additional studying personnel in 2023 to achieve the goals set by the new contract. This means that including data after 2022 will be misleading for judging the effect of the geospatial ticketing system on productivity except if significant manual work is conducted in order to isolate and remove the newly inserted factors in relation to previous years (i.e. vegetation management studies, additional personnel etc). Thus, it was decided to conclude and move forward with the publication of results for years 2021 and 2022. To avoid getting misleading results from the past, only data from 2020 was included in the analysis. This was done as it was easy to verify that the 2020 data was equivalent to 2021 and 2022 data, with all affecting factors being more or less identical. However, as one moved further in the past, it was increasingly possible that factors affecting the results would vary and thus comparing the

results from more years could be misleading. For example, personnel working with network studies had been moved from NECS some years prior to 2020 and vegetation management works were included in the dataset of certain years prior to 2020.

Geospatial systems have been used in a variety of power network applications (e.g. [14-19]), but the approach presented initially in [7] and further investigated in this work differs for two main reasons: that it is based on free to use web tools and that it incorporates a ticket management aspect. Thus, it is easy to be implemented by other utilities or organizations that wish to boost their productivity without increasing costs or significantly altering their infrastructure and mode of operation (providing that certain characteristics of their work is similar to the ones presented here i.e. they cover a wide geographic area and face a variety of issues).

V. CONCLUSION

This paper focuses on the effect that a geospatial ticket management system had on the productivity of the network studies subsection of the Network Engineering & Construction Section (NECS) of HEDNO's Patras Area, Greece. The system and relative background has been thoroughly presented in [7] whereas the current work focuses on investigating the results on productivity after two years of operation. Some updates and improvements made on the system over the last two years are also briefly presented. Two different values were considered to measure productivity: the number of conducted studies and the accumulated predicted labor cost of these studies. This was done in order to acquire a better view on the actual effect of the system and to avoid misleading assumptions. Both these values exhibit a similar increase (40.82% and 41.39% respectively) over the past two years. Since, the other contributing factors (personnel, workhours etc) have remained largely unchanged over these years, it is strongly hinted that the system had a significant effect on the productivity of the subsection. Considering that the system is based on free to use software (mainly Google Maps) it is thus proposed that similar systems can be utilized to increase the productivity of any utility or organization that covers a wide geographical area and faces a variety of issues.

REFERENCES

- [1] T. J. Coelli, D. S. Prasada Rao, C. J. O' Donnell, G. E. Battese, *An introduction to efficiency and productivity analysis*, 2nd ed., USA: Springer, 2005.
- [2] J. Sauermann, "Performance measures and worker productivity," *IZA World of Labor*, pp. 1-12, 2023, Art. no. 260, <https://doi.org/10.15185/izawol.260.v2>.
- [3] M. H. Momade and M. R. Hainin, "Identifying Motivational and Demotivational Productivity Factors in Qatar Construction Projects," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 3945-3948, Apr. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2577>.
- [4] C. Tengey, N. I. Nwulu, O. Adepoju, and O. M. Longe, "Analysis of the Productivity Dynamics of Electricity Distribution Regions in Ghana," *Energies*, vol. 15, no. 24, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 9414, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15249414>.
- [5] F. J. Ramos-Real, B. Tovar, M. Iooty, E. F. de Almeida, and H. Q. Pinto, "The evolution and main determinants of productivity in Brazilian electricity distribution 1998-2005: An empirical analysis," *Energy*

- Economics*, vol 31, no. 2, pp. 298-305, 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2008.11.002>.
- [6] L.-C. Chen, W.-M. Lu, and C. Yang, "Does Knowledge Management Matter? Assessing the Performance of Electricity Distribution Districts Based on Slacks-Based Data Envelopment Analysis," *The Journal of the Operational Research Society*, vol. 60, no. 11, pp. 1583-1593, Nov. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1057/jors.2008.182>.
- [7] D. Pylarinos, "Using Google My Maps as a Geospatial Ticket Management System for Scheduling and Monitoring Power Distribution Network Works: Case Study of Patras Area's Distribution Network Engineering & Construction Section," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 8143-8150, Feb. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4642>.
- [8] S. A. Fenrick, L. Getachew, "Cost and reliability comparisons of underground and overhead power lines," *Utilities Policy*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 31-37, 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jup.2011.10.002>.
- [9] A. B. L. Paredes, *The Decision on Overhead or Underground Power Cables: An Economic Analysis of E-Redes Investment Projects. Internship Report*. University of Porto, 2022.
- [10] K. McCarthy, "Undergrounding Electric Lines," OLR Research Report 2011-R-0338, Oct. 2011. [Online]. Available: <https://www.cga.ct.gov/2011/rpt/2011-R-0338.htm>.
- [11] "Guaranteed Services to Consumers," *HEDNO*. <https://deddie.gr/en/eggymenes-ypirisies-katanaloton/>.
- [12] HEDNO, *Compliance Program*. Athens, Greece: HEDNO, 2014.
- [13] HEDNO, *Volume of Changes in Relation to ND-219*. Athens, Greece: HEDNO, 2021.
- [14] D. Pylarinos and I. Pellas, "Incorporating Open/Free GIS and GPS Software in Power Transmission Line Routine Work: The Case of Crete and Rhodes," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1316-1322, Feb. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1182>.
- [15] F. Elmahmoudi, O. E. K. Abra, A. Raihani, O. Serrar, and L. Bahatti, "Elaboration of a Wind Energy Potential Map in Morocco using GIS and Analytic Hierarchy Process," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 6068-6075, Aug. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3692>.
- [16] T. Eldamaty, A. G. Ahmed, and M. M. Helal, "GIS-Based Multi Criteria Analysis for Solar Power Plant Site Selection Support in Mecca," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 10963-10968, Jun. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5927>.
- [17] G.-G. Hognogi, A.-M. Pop, A.-C. Marian-Potra, and T. Somesfalean, "The Role of UAS-GIS in Digital Era Governance. A Systematic Literature Review," *Sustainability*, vol. 13, no. 19, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 11097, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su131911097>.
- [18] Y. Yang, Y.-F. Liu, and Y.-L. Cao, "Study on a method of design for rural power distribution lines based on 3D GIS technology," *Mathematical and Computer Modelling*, vol. 51, no. 11, pp. 1293-1298, Jun. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mcm.2009.10.033>.
- [19] A. Bosisio, M. Moncecchi, A. Morotti, and M. Merlo, "Machine Learning and GIS Approach for Electrical Load Assessment to Increase Distribution Networks Resilience," *Energies*, vol. 14, no. 14, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 4133, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14144133>.

Development and Application of Linear Variable Differential Transformer (LVDT) Sensors for the Structural Health Monitoring of an Urban Railway Bridge in Vietnam

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ABSTRACT

Measuring the structure's displacement plays a very important role in ensuring the safe operation of railway bridges in general and urban railway bridges in particular. In Vietnam, traditional methods using high-precision mechanical gauges have been used to measure the displacement of railway bridges. However, these methods need a lot of effort in installation and traffic control during implementation. These methods are based on the static principle: The test loads are placed on the bridge structure, and then the structure's displacement is observed. The safety assessment and analysis results are guaranteed by multiplying the dynamic coefficients, leading to some assessments that may not be close to the actual exploitation of the bridge structure. Therefore, the current study presents a new solution for measuring the displacement of railway bridge structures. This method uses Linear Variable Differential Transformer (LVDT) sensors to record the continuous displacement of the structure during the time the train passes over the bridge. Through field measurements combined with a finite element analysis model, the research focuses on developing and applying LVDT sensors in urban railway bridge structure health monitoring. At the same time, the potential of developing this method in Vietnam in the future is evaluated.

Keywords-dynamic displacement; LVDT; urban railway

I. INTRODUCTION

The urban railway is considered the backbone of the transport infrastructure system of any developed city in the world [1, 2]. Hanoi is no exception. Moreover, the need to build an urban railway network is becoming more urgent than ever when the pressure of traffic congestion and environmental pollution increasingly weighs on the narrow infrastructure fund of the Vietnamese capital. Putting into operation the urban railway network is expected not only to change the urban appearance of Hanoi and reduce congestion and accidents, but to a greater extent, it will change the habit of using public transport and the traffic culture of the people in the future. Currently, Hanoi is expected to have 8 urban railway lines totaling about 318 km. This is the first elevated urban railway system in Vietnam. The first two railway lines built were Line 2A, section Cat Linh - Ha Dong, and Line 3, section Nhon - Hanoi Railway Station. Therefore, timely detection and repair of problems related to the span structure are extremely necessary because the route is built in the roadway of densely populated and high-traffic routes, making repairs on a large scale difficult. One of the causes affecting the damage of partial span structures is also due to excessive deformation. In the management and understanding of both new infrastructure using new technologies and decaying infrastructure, in particular bridges and pavements, field testing is a topic that is becoming more and more crucial. After an isolated and potentially catastrophic event, there is a requirement for precise and expensive diagnostics, load distribution verification, actual load-carrying capacity calculation, and structural performance evaluation. This helps to improve the efficiency of exploitation and increase the safety of railway infrastructure. At the same time, the regular assessment will take timely remedial measures to avoid disrupting traffic and not affecting other related industries.

Railroad managers inspect bridges regularly to ensure their safety and prevent derailments, delays in network operation, and loss of time and resources. The majority of contemporary bridge inspection techniques call for visual inspection [3] which often is not reliable [4-6]. The operational capacities of a bridge can be determined with the help of Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) [7]. Railroad management organizations are interested in measuring parameters and responses under loads to objectively inform the safety and expansion of their operations. An essential component of SHM is the measurement of bridge displacement under dynamic loads brought on by train motion [8-10]. The measured deflection response can be incorporated into a bridge finite element model to calculate back residual capacity, compare the in-service behavior with the intended behavior, or determine the degree of damage. According to the commonly used traditional method, displacement at a position on the structure is measured through static testing. The load is calculated and placed in the most unfavorable position of the structure [11, 12]. The equipment used here is high-precision mechanical gauges or high-precision surveying devices (Figure 1). The above method has relatively accurate results for the test loads. However, there are a few shortcomings in this method. First, in order to perform the static load test, it is necessary to stop the traffic on the road (Figure 2). Second, the measured result is the displacement

caused by the test load, not the actual daily load on the bridge. The test load is completely based on the experience and the calculations of the consultant. Therefore, the results do not fully evaluate the entire response of the bridge. Furthermore, this result only represents a specified moment of the bridge, which is usually the maximum value when the test load enters the bridge. If an abnormality is present in the dynamic response, this result will usually not be accurately evaluated [13].

Fig. 1. Measure displacement: (a) Use of high-precision mechanical gauges, (b). surveying devices.

Fig. 2. Static load test to inspection bridge.

In railway bridges, especially urban railway bridges, it is impossible to mobilize test loads from trains. The only way to measure displacement of a bridge structure is to measure it during its operation. Traditional methods are not efficient enough and the obtained results will not have high accuracy. This leads to the need to apply a new type of device to record the dynamic displacement of the structure under the effect of operating loads. Several researchers have developed methods for different types of devices. Authors in [14-16] used accelerometers to measure the horizontal displacement of the structure. The Global Positioning System (GPS) has also been used as a contact sensor to measure displacement [17-19]. Although these methods are relatively modern, the accuracy level is only acceptable. Besides, the equipment investment cost for the above solutions is relatively expensive, often not suitable for management units.

LVDT has been applied to many projects around the world [20], even though in Vietnam, this device is still in limited use. This study proposes the use of LVDT sensors installed on the urban railway bridge structure to measure the displacement under the effect of the train load in operation. System validation and development were conducted through field experiments and finite element modeling. Finally, barriers to using LVDT for field applications were identified and possible solutions to each problem were proposed.

II. LINEAR VARIABLE DIFFERENTIAL TRANSFORMER (LVDT)

A. Introducing LVDT

The LVDT is an essential kind of inductive transducer. Inductive transducers are those that operate on the idea of a transduction mechanism. In essence, an LVDT is a position sensor that can pick up on linear motion or vibrations and translate them into electrical signals or a fluctuating electrical current. The LVDT sensor transforms the linear movement of the object to which it is connected into a variable electrical signal that corresponds to that movement. The movement might range from 0-0.5 mm to 0-1000 mm in laboratory, industrial, and underwater contexts. This design has been in use for many years for the precise measurement of displacement and for positioning control in tight loops.

B. The LVDT Working Principle

Similar to a transformer, an LVDT has one main winding, designated P, and two secondary windings, designated S1 and S2. The primary and secondary windings are wound on a former, which is a hollow cylindrical structure (Figure 3). The former is frequently made of glass-reinforced polymer that has been clad in cylindrical steel and wrapped in a porous material. The primary winding of the cylindrical former is in the middle, and on either side of it, two secondary windings are placed evenly separated from the center. Both secondary windings have the same number of turns and are connected to one another in series opposition, meaning that they are wound in different directions yet are connected to one another.

Fig. 3. Structure of LVDT

The electromagnetic law of Faraday serves as the foundation for how LVDTs function. An alternating magnetic field is produced when the primary winding of the LVDT is connected to the AC power source; this field generates an electromotive force (emf) in the secondary windings. The

secondary signal alters as the core moves in this region (Figure 4(a)). When the core is positioned in the center and the two secondary windings are arranged and connected in a specified configuration (push-pull mode), a zero signal is obtained. The signal grows as the core is moved away from this location in either direction (Figure 4(b)). The signal output has a linear relationship with the actual mechanical movement of the core as long as the windings are wound with a specific level of precision. A phase-sensitive demodulator that switches at the same frequency as the primary energizing supply then processes the secondary output signal. This yields a final output that, following rectification and filtering, provides a DC or 4-20 mA output proportional to the core movement and also specifies its direction, positive or negative from the center zero point (Figure 4(c)).

Fig. 4. The LVDT working principle.

C. Advantages of the LVDT

One of the most outstanding features of the LVDT over other mechanical measuring devices is the absence of friction. This is because there is no direct contact between the moving core and the other parts. This results in the device not being easily damaged. In terms of longevity, LVDT will be more durable than other devices. The LVDT does not need to employ an amplifier to amplify the signals because of its powerful output signal and sensitivity to even very small displacements. This is very suitable for monitoring and measuring structures with large displacements such as bridges. They typically use less than 1 W of electricity and exhibit less hysteresis loss, which improves their reliability. LVDT sensors are small and lightweight, they can be readily handled and aligned to meet requirements. In spite of their tiny size and lightweight nature,

LVDT can withstand mechanical shocks and vibrations. The absolute value is provided by the LVDT. It implies that in the event of an unexpected power outage, the LVDT does not lose its location data. If the measurement is redone, the output value stays the same as it was before to the power outage.

From the above advantages, the application and development of LVDT in dynamic measurement and monitoring of urban railway bridge structures is completely appropriate.

III. CASE STUDY

A. Hanoi Urban Railway, Cat Linh Ha Dong Line

The Hanoi Urban Railway system includes the urban railway line connecting Cat Linh and Ha Dong (Figure 5). The Cat Linh - Ha Dong route has a total length of 13021.48 m. The entire route is built on high (overpass form). The main span structure used is a combination of simple beams supported on piers. The span length main forms are 18.5, 20, 26, 29, 30, 32 m span structure with box cross section. Cat Linh - Ha Dong urban railway line is designed to ensure a harmonious connection with other urban railway lines in the future and bus stations along the route.

Fig. 5. The Cat Linh-Ha Dong urban railway bridge.

B. Equipment Selection

As described above, the equipment used here is two LVDT sensors and dedicated cables for signal transmission (Figure 6).

Fig. 6. LVDT sensors and cables.

In addition to the main part, LVDT displacement sensors, accessories such as jigs, and fixing devices are also equipped. A dedicated computer is used throughout the entire experiment. To ensure the objectivity of the measurement results, a number of mechanical devices have been used and verified in many experiments (high-precision mechanical gauges).

C. Field test

At the center of a box girder span, a mechanical measuring device and an LVDT sensor are installed (Figure 7).

Fig. 7. Installation of the measuring equipment: (a) high-precision mechanical gauges, (b) LVDT sensor, (c) data recording.

A laptop is used with integrated measurement software NI-LabVIEW 2014 (32-bit). It collects signals from the measuring heads during measurement and saves them as files. Displacement is measured in both vertical and horizontal direction of the structure.

D. Creation of the Finite Element Model

Fig. 8. The finite element model of the structure.

A finite element model was built based on the surveyed conditions and the profile of the project. The simulated mobile load is a train moving at the speed according to the operating profile. The elements used are in the form of beams, the load is the moving load of the train.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The simulation and experimental results are shown in Figures 9 and 10.

Fig. 9. Vertical displacement results. (a) Simulation, (b) experiment.

Fig. 10. Horizontal displacement results. (a) Simulation, (b) experiment.

Based on the results obtained from the model and the experiment, it can be seen that the measurement results from the LVDT and the model are similar. The LVDT sensor allows to record structural displacement data during the entire time the train is acting on the structure. Meanwhile, high-precision

mechanical gauges only allow a maximum value to be observed. The comparison results between the model, the LVDT sensor and the high-precision mechanical gauges are similar, showing the reliability of the LVDT sensor. The maximum vertical displacement value in the obtained model is 5.48 mm, LVDT is 5.68 mm, and high-precision mechanical gauges are 5.5 mm. Because it is done automatically and has a higher sensitivity than human observation to mechanical equipment, LVDT gives more accurate results.

V. CONCLUSION

Structural displacement measurement plays a significant role in ensuring the safe operation of urban railway bridges. This study proposes the use of LVDT sensors in structural health monitoring (specifically displacement monitoring) on urban railway bridges. The displacement monitoring by LVDT is applied and gives good results on the actual bridge. Field tests are designed for the application and development of LVDT in structural displacement monitoring. The experiment confirms the accuracy of the applied method and is combined with the results of the finite element simulation. Through testing on a real bridge, the obtained results show the potential of LVDT when applied outside the laboratory. Although the initial investment cost may seem higher than that of traditional solutions, when it comes to long-term and performance aspects, the LVDT shows its effectiveness when applied in practice. Here are some of the main conclusions of the current study:

- Applying LVDT in continuous displacement monitoring of structures gives better results than other traditional methods. The obtained results are similar to the modeling results and the accuracy is greater than that of the traditional methods used in Vietnam.
- The result from LVDT is in the form of continuous data, and not discrete as when using high-precision mechanical gauges. This leads to the easy observation of structural irregularities over long periods of time
- The results obtained from LVDT can be used for big data applications in structural health monitoring. Specifically, time series data can be used as an input to train artificial intelligence networks that are being developed recently.

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REFERENCES

- [1] D. D. Van, "A Research on the Load Calculation Method in Designing the Traction Power Supply for Integrated Subway – MCR," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 10882–10887, Jun. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5909>.
- [2] A. Z. Bulum, M. Dugenci, and M. Ipek, "Application of a Seat-based Booking Control Mechanism in Rail Transport with Customer Diversion," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 9126–9135, Oct. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5171>.

- [3] *How Freight Railroads Maintain Bridges*. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OJfWv_ZwNk, 2013.
- [4] D. Agdas, J. A. Rice, J. R. Martinez, and I. R. Lasa, "Comparison of Visual Inspection and Structural-Health Monitoring As Bridge Condition Assessment Methods," *Journal of Performance of Constructed Facilities*, vol. 30, no. 3, Jun. 2016, Art. no. 04015049, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)CF.1943-5509.0000802](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)CF.1943-5509.0000802).
- [5] N. T. C. Nguyen, M. Q. Tran, H. S. Sousa, T. V. Ngo, and J. C. Matos, "Damage detection of structural based on indirect vibration measurement results combined with Artificial Neural Network," *Journal of Materials and Engineering Structures*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 403–410, Dec. 2022.
- [6] T. Q. Minh, S. S. Helder, and C. M. Jose, "Application of AI Tools in Creating Datasets from A Real Data Component for Structural Health Monitoring," in *Data Driven Methods for Civil Structural Health Monitoring and Resilience: Latest Developments and Applications*, CRC Press, 2023.
- [7] M. S. Mohammed and K. Ki-Seong, "Chirplet Transform in Ultrasonic Non-Destructive Testing and Structural Health Monitoring: A Review," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 3778–3781, Feb. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2470>.
- [8] F. Moreu and J. M. LaFave, "Current Research Topics: Railroad Bridges and Structural Engineering," University of Illinois, Newmark Structural Engineering Laboratory Report Series Report No. NSEL-032, Oct. 2012.
- [9] T. Q. Minh, N. T. C. Nhung, N. H. Quyet, S. Helder, S. Sou, and C. J. Matos, "Opportunities and Challenges of Digital Twins in Structural Health Monitoring," in *Proceedings of the 4th International Conference on Sustainability in Civil Engineering*, Hanoi, Vietnam, Nov. 2023, pp. 25–27.
- [10] N. T. C. Nguyen, M. Q. Tran, H. S. Sousa, T. V. Ngo, and J. C. Matos, "Damage detection of structural based on indirect vibration measurement results combined with Artificial Neural Network," *Journal of Materials and Engineering Structures « JMES »*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 403–410, Dec. 2022.
- [11] M. Q. Tran *et al.*, "Structural Assessment Based on Vibration Measurement Test Combined with an Artificial Neural Network for the Steel Truss Bridge," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 13, no. 13, Jan. 2023, Art. no. 7484, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13137484>.
- [12] M. Q. Tran, H. S. Sousa, J. Matos, S. Fernandes, Q. T. Nguyen, and S. N. Dang, "Finite Element Model Updating for Composite Plate Structures Using Particle Swarm Optimization Algorithm," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 13, no. 13, an. 2023, Art. no. 7719, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13137719>.
- [13] C. Dong, S. Bas, M. Debees, N. Alver, and F. N. Catbas, "Bridge Load Testing for Identifying Live Load Distribution, Load Rating, Serviceability and Dynamic Response," *Frontiers in Built Environment*, vol. 6, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbuil.2020.00046>.
- [14] J. Yang, J. B. Li, and G. Lin, "A simple approach to integration of acceleration data for dynamic soil–structure interaction analysis," *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, vol. 26, no. 8, pp. 725–734, Aug. 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soildyn.2005.12.011>.
- [15] T. Nagayama, B. F. Spencer, and J. A. Rice, "Structural health monitoring using smart sensors," in *World Forum on Smart Materials and Smart Structures Technology*, CRC Press, 2008.
- [16] A. I. Ozdagli, F. Moreu, J. A. Gomez, P. Garp, and S. Vemuganti, "Data Fusion of Accelerometers with Inclometers for Reference-free High Fidelity Displacement Estimation," presented at the 8th European Workshop On Structural Health Monitoring (EWSHM 2016), Bilbao, Spain, Jul. 2016.
- [17] T.-L. Wang, V. K. Garg, and K.-H. Chu, "Railway Bridge/Vehicle Interaction Studies with New Vehicle Model," *Journal of Structural Engineering*, vol. 117, no. 7, pp. 2099–2116, Jul. 1991, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9445\(1991\)117:7\(2099\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9445(1991)117:7(2099)).
- [18] X. Meng, A. H. Dodson, and G. W. Roberts, "Detecting bridge dynamics with GPS and triaxial accelerometers," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 29, no. 11, pp. 3178–3184, Nov. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2007.03.012>.
- [19] T.-H. Yi, H.-N. Li, and M. Gu, "Experimental assessment of high-rate GPS receivers for deformation monitoring of bridge," *Measurement*, vol. 46, no. 1, pp. 420–432, Jan. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measurement.2012.07.018>.
- [20] F. Moreu *et al.*, "Dynamic Assessment of Timber Railroad Bridges Using Displacements," *Journal of Bridge Engineering*, vol. 20, no. 10, Oct. 2015, Art. no. 04014114, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)BE.1943-5592.0000726](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)BE.1943-5592.0000726).

Application of Seasonal Trend Decomposition using Loess and Long Short-Term Memory in Peak Load Forecasting Model in Tien Giang

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ABSTRACT

Daily peak load forecasting is critical for energy providers to meet the loads of grid-connected consumers. This study proposed a Seasonal Trend decomposition using Loess combined with Long Short-Term Memory (STL-LTSM) method and compared its performance on peak forecasting of electrical energy demand with Convolutional Neural Network and LSTM (CNN-LSTM), Wavenet, and the classic approaches Artificial Neural Network (ANN) and LSTM. The study evaluated the models using demand data from the power system in Tien Giang province, Vietnam, from 2020 to 2022, considering historical demand, holidays, and weather variables as input characteristics. The results showed that the proposed STL-LSTM model can predict future demand with lower Base Mean Square Error (RMSE) and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE). Therefore, the proposed method can help energy suppliers make smart decisions and plan for future demand.

Keywords-Wavenet; LSTM; CNN; STL; peak load forecasting

I. INTRODUCTION

In current development trends, technology occupies an increasingly large part of life. Thus, the electricity demand is increasing rapidly along with the development of microgrids [1]. Microgrid models in the form of a small-scale power grid with advanced techniques and tools are designed for optimal energy operation [2]. The importance of consumer load forecasting is increasingly emphasized [3]. The problem of forecasting peak loads is considered complicated. Accurate short-term forecast results support efficient and convenient operation and exploitation of a power system in an area. If the prediction indicates that the storage capacity is insufficient to support future loads, the power company may notify users of this status, causing them to reduce their electricity usage. In [4],

a hybrid approach was proposed for short-term forecasting of load demand in a typical microgrid, which was a combination of a static wavelet packet transform and a feedforward neural network based on the Harris Hawks Optimization (HHO) algorithm. HHO is applied to a feedforward neural network as an alternative training algorithm to optimize the weights and basis of neurons. In [5], Wavenet with dilating causal complexes and connection skip was used to work with long-term information, presenting various advantages compared to other statistical algorithms.

Many forecasting methods have been proposed to solve the load forecasting problem. These approaches are classified as statistical, persistence, machine learning, and association approaches [4]. In [7], a multiple linear regression model was presented to predict the hourly basic load demand [8], using the

trial-and-error method to determine the appropriate structure of the proposed model. A regression-based moving window with an adjustable window size-based method was presented in [9]. This method was compared with a Back-Propagation-based Neural Network (BPNN) to show the effectiveness of the regression-based moving window strategy. In [10], load forecasting was carried out in a microgrid using the persistence method. In [11-12], a Kalman filter-based model was proposed to forecast the short-term load demand of a household, comparing its performance with existing competing methods. Other models, such as autoregressive moving average with exogenous variables (ARMAX) [13-14], Auto-Regression Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) [15], Seasonal ARIMA (SARIMA) [16], and modified autoregressive moving average (ARMA) [17], were suggested for short-term load forecasting. However, these methods were not capable of handling nonlinear load characteristics, limiting their application.

Machine learning and composite approaches are considered to be powerful techniques for dealing with the nonlinear properties of loads. Machine learning approaches include Support Vector Machines (SVMs) and Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) [18]. In [19-22], decomposition with Loess forecasting (STLF) was carried out by applying both SVM and a seasonally adjusted SVM-based association model (SSA-SVM). SSA-SVM was compared with seasonally integrated wavelet-based ANN and simple ANN, showing its superior performance. Several combined approaches were applied to load forecasting, such as SVM-based Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) [23], Genetic Algorithm (GA) with SVM [24], firefly algorithm (FFA) SVM [25-26], SVM-based Grasshopper Optimization Algorithm (GOA) [27], improved fruit fly optimization algorithm based on SVM [28], horizontal movement algorithm based on hybrid PSO and SVM [29], Experimental Mode Decomposition (EMD) [30], and Wavelet Transform (WT) with PSO-SVM [31]. Least Squares SVM (LSSVM) is an improved type of SVM that has also been applied to load forecasting. In [32], LSSVM and LSSVM with PSO for STLF were compared with conventional approaches to demonstrate their effectiveness. A hybrid WT with Fruit Fly Optimization (FFO) and a sperm whale-based LSSVM algorithm were proposed in [33] for STLF, showing outstanding performance.

The machine learning methods have some disadvantages, such as difficulty in parameter selection and unclear choice of input variables. This study proposed an improved peak load forecasting approach using the Seasonal Trend decomposition using Loess (STL) combined with LSTM (STL-LSTM). The proposed STL-LSTM method was compared with some other competing models, such as ANN, LSTM, CNN-LSTM, and Wavenet, to evaluate its performance.

II. THE PROPOSED ALGORITHM

A. Methodology

1) Seasonal Trend Decomposition Using Loess (STL)

STL is a statistical technique that decomposes a time series into three parts: seasonality, trend, and residual [2]. It uses the locally weighted regression method, commonly known as

Loess, to identify seasonal components and trends, while residuals are calculated by subtracting seasonal components and estimated trends from the initial time series. The trend component represents the long-term trend of the time series, while the seasonal component represents cyclical variations. Finally, the residual component captures fluctuations that cannot be predicted. The third panel of Figure 1 shows a seasonal component, with data variation of one cycle per year. The residual component, shown in the fourth panel of Figure 1, is the remaining variation in the data beyond the seasonal and trend components. Suppose that Y_t is the value of the time series, S_t is the value of the seasonal component, T_t is the value of the trend component, and R_t is the value of the residual component at point t , for $t = 1 \dots n$. The three components of STL analysis relate to the raw time series as follows:

$$Y_t = S_t + T_t + R_t \quad (1)$$

In previous studies, the STL method was applied to separate the data into three distinct parts, which were independently analyzed for training, validation, and testing sets. These components were used to predict the upcoming values of the time series.

Fig. 1. Extracted samples of hourly and weekly seasonal components.

2) Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)

LSTM is a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) architecture that has gained popularity due to its ability to effectively handle long-term dependencies in sequential data. Unlike traditional RNNs, LSTM uses gates and memory cells to selectively retain or forget information from previous time steps. This unique mechanism prevents the vanishing gradient problem commonly encountered in RNNs. Moreover, LSTMs are well suited for tasks that require modeling long-term dependencies, thanks to their capability to store information over extended periods. Numerous studies on load forecasting have demonstrated the efficiency of LSTM networks [9].

Time-series data plays a crucial role in power load analysis. When it comes to time-series forecasting, RNNs offer distinct advantages compared to feedforward neural networks. However, RNNs face two primary challenges during training. Firstly, as training progresses further into the past, the influence of the gradient signal diminishes, making it less effective for capturing long-term dependencies. This issue is commonly known as the gradient vanishing problem. Second, at each training step, the gradient must be calculated for the activation function. If the result exceeds one, the gradient update grows exponentially, particularly with an increasing number of layers, leading to a gradient explosion.

This study proposes a load forecasting model based on LSTM neural networks as a solution to the limitations of RNNs. LSTM networks are an enhanced version of RNNs, featuring a distinctive structure. The RNN network comprises a repeating module with a straightforward design, as shown in Figure 2. Each module in the RNN network includes a single layer. On the other hand, the LSTM network shares a structure similar to the RNN, except for the presence of the memory cell module, as illustrated in Figure 3. In contrast to the single-layer architecture of RNNs, LSTM neural networks involve four distinct interacting layers.

Fig. 2. The chain of RNN.

Fig. 3. The chain of LSTM neural network.

The LSTM neural network model has four parts: an input, an output, a forget, and an update part, as shown in Figure 3. In Figure 3, x_t is multiplied by f_t . The unimportant information x_t represents the input at time t , h_t represents the hidden state at time t , c_t represents the cell state at time t , and σ denotes a logistic sigmoid function that returns a probability value between zero and one, indicating the possibility of signal transmission. A value of 0 indicates that the signal cannot pass, while 1 indicates that all signals are allowed to pass.

Each cell in an LSTM network has a complex structure, controlled by three gates: a forget, an input, and an output.

Cells manipulate information in the network using these three gates to remove or add information to the cell state c_t , i.e. "memory". The forget gate determines the forgetting level, as shown in Figure 4(a), f_t representing the gate control switch of the forget gate, which controls the number of forgotten previous cell states. Similarly to human memory, a forget gate can perform the function of forgetting unimportant information while retaining important information.

$$f_t = \sigma(W_f[h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_f) \tag{2}$$

Figure 4(b) shows the input port that receives new information from the peripheral input and chooses to remember the information in the current state and the data in the previously hidden state. This creates a new vector to hold the data, which can be updated. In the input port, the tanh class defines the candidate value of the updated content and the sigmoid class defines the updated content. The probability value ranges from 0 to 1.

$$i_t = \sigma(W_i[h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_i) \tag{3}$$

$$\tilde{c}_t = \tanh(W_c[h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_c) \tag{4}$$

The next step involves updating the cell state, as shown in Figure 4(c). This process is as follows. At first, c_{t-1} is multiplied by f_t . Then the unimportant information is forgotten and the important information is retained. Finally, the information remaining in the current input is retained to obtain the latest cell state. This step varies depending on how updated each state is:

$$c_t = f_t \cdot c_{t-1} + i_t \cdot \tilde{c}_t \tag{5}$$

The sigmoid layer in the output gate defines the output from the current cell state, as shown in Figure 4(d). This process is performed using the tanh function. The output of the sigmoid layer is then multiplied by the processed value between -1 and 1 to obtain the output. Finally, the output gate switches the c_t cell state, and the obtained h_t output to the next cell is calculated as follows:

$$o_t = \sigma(W_o[h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_o) \tag{6}$$

$$h_t = o_t \cdot \tanh(c_{t-1}) \tag{7}$$

where W_f , W_i , W_c , and W_o are the weight matrices of forget gate, input port, cell state, and output port, respectively, and b_f , b_i , b_c , and b_o are the bias vectors, respectively.

The traditional LSTM neural network model solves the problem of n -step prediction by adding a thick layer when providing the h_t output. This maps the hidden state to an n -dimensional vector, which in turn responds to the data format of the problem. The n steps are predicted completely independently at this point. Therefore, string dependencies between output labels are not considered when using LSTM for prediction. Furthermore, LSTM cannot support variable-length input. If a sensor suddenly crashes during monitoring, resulting in partial loss of predictive data, LSTM may not complete the training. These limitations can be addressed by employing the proposed model for electric load forecasting, which combines STL with LSTM. Figure 5 shows this sequential approach method.

Fig. 4. Structure of a cell in an LSTM neural network: (a) Forget gate, (b) input port, (c) status update section, and (d) output port.

Fig. 5. Flowchart of the STL-LSTM model.

The dataset was first normalized between 0 and 1 using the Min-Max-Scaler for LSTM analysis. Then a lookback window of 1 was applied, where the input sequence was a sliding window of time steps and the output was a single value. The data were reshaped to fit the input geometry of the LSTM layer. This model consists of a hidden layer with 64 units, followed by a density output layer with a linear activation function. The model was compiled using the Adam optimizer and the mean-squared loss function. The model was trained and validated using prepared training and validation datasets. During training, the model's loss and the validation loss were used to evaluate its performance.

B. Experiment

1) Dataset

A dataset on the electric load of Tiền Giang province, Vietnam, from 2020 to 2022 was used to evaluate the proposed method. Figure 6 shows some sample data. To address the problem of load forecasting, in addition to demand periodicity, factors that affect power consumption were considered. In addition to the periodicity of demand, weather factors such as outdoor temperature, humidity, solar irradiance, and wind speed during the day were included. Time factors such as festivals or economic factors play an important role in the accurate prediction of loads. However, the collection of these external factors is very complicated, and the collected data are usually expressed as continuous and cyclic time series during

the day. This study evaluated data by timeline, time coding by day, week, month, holiday, and local outdoor temperature for the corresponding period. Figure 7 shows the temperature (in °C, orange) and electrical load (in kWh, blue) in Tien Giang for the corresponding time in a day.

Fig. 6. Electricity load data for a week in Tien Giang.

Fig. 7. Electricity and temperature data for a week in Tien Giang.

It can be seen that the load profile is significantly influenced by the temperature data variation. Therefore, the outdoor temperature acts as a highly correlated factor with the electrical load data. During the tests, the input data was normalized to the interval [0, 1]. Furthermore, 80% of the data was used for training and the remaining 20% was used for testing. These data were processed to predict the maximum daily load. Figure 8 shows daily peak data with seasonal features.

Fig. 8. Observations, trends, seasons, and residuals of peak demand.

2) Evaluation Indicators

Five metrics were used to evaluate the predictive performance of the T-GCN model on Y_t and the predicted \hat{Y}_t : Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), Accuracy, coefficient of determination (R^2), and explained variance score (Var). The following equations show the calculation formulas:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n (Y_t - \hat{Y}_t)^2} \tag{8}$$

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n |Y_t - \hat{Y}_t| \tag{9}$$

$$Accuracy = 1 - \frac{\|Y - \hat{Y}\|_F}{\|Y\|_F} \tag{10}$$

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{n(RMSE)^2}{\sum_{t=1}^n (Y_t - \bar{Y})^2} \tag{11}$$

$$Var = 1 - \frac{Var\{Y - \hat{Y}\}}{Var\{Y\}} \tag{12}$$

RMSE and MAE are used to measure prediction error, while their smaller values indicate greater accuracy. Accuracy is used to detect the accuracy of the prediction, and higher values indicate greater accuracy. R^2 and Var measure the ability of the predicted results to represent the actual data, and larger values indicate better prediction accuracy. To assess the effectiveness

of the LSTM model, the Training loss over the training epochs was examined, as shown in Figure 9.

Fig. 9. Training loss of the LSTM model through the number of iterations.

3) Error Evaluation Results

Table I shows the performance of the models evaluated. The proposed model performed better in most criteria. The RMSE and MAPE coefficients clearly show the superiority of the proposed STL-LSTM method, as it scored lower values.

TABLE I. FORECAST RESULTS

Model	RMSE	MAPE (%)
ANN	1509.5	6.34
LSTM	730.87	4.96
CNN-LSTM	359.18	2.08
Wavenet	298.93	1.66
STL-LSTM	292.53	1.52

According to the results in Table I, the forecasting model using ANN gave the highest error results. The LSTM model and the CNN-LSTM gave better MAPE of 4.96% and 2.08%, respectively. In the Wavenet pattern, MAPE dropped significantly to 1.66 and had an RMSE of 298.93. Overall, the results demonstrate that the integration of STL with LSTM significantly improved forecasting accuracy, as its MAPE of 1.52% and RMSE of 292.53 indicate that it produced highly accurate forecasts, with significantly lower errors.

The superiority of the proposed STL-LSTM model demonstrates that it could be a promising approach to time-series forecasting and capture of correlated characteristics that can be decomposed into seasonal and trend components. However, further analysis and validation on different datasets and periods are necessary to confirm its generalizability and robustness.

4) Forecast Graph Results

Figure 10 displays the forecast results, showing the actual (blue) and forecast (red) data. The proposed STL-LSTM method exhibited better accuracy since the forecast results and the actual data almost coincide. The other methods had large errors, showing greater divergence between the actual and forecast data.

Fig. 10. Comparison of actual value and proposed STL-LSTM network aggregation method.

III. CONCLUSION

The presented results show that the proposed STL-LSTM method had improved performance in terms of *MAPE* and *RMSE*. By integrating STL and LSTM, the model can capture both short-term and long-term variations in the time series, while preserving the ability to model the seasonal component of the data. This integration is particularly beneficial for forecasting seasonal time series, where the method needs to accurately predict both seasonal and non-seasonal components. In summary, integrating STL into LSTM enables the model to learn both the seasonal and noise components, resulting in improved forecasting performance. This approach can lead to better results in time series forecasting tasks. However, a drawback of the proposed STL-LSTM model is that its algorithm is more computationally intensive and time-consuming than the other compared methods. In the future, the algorithm will be expanded to be able to optimize multiple values at the same time and reduce its computational resource consumption, while maintaining or improving its performance.

REFERENCES

- [1] N. Ahmad, Y. Ghadi, M. Adnan, and M. Ali, "Load Forecasting Techniques for Power System: Research Challenges and Survey," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 71054–71090, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3187839>.
- [2] M. Fan, Y. Hu, X. Zhang, H. Yin, Q. Yang, and L. Fan, "Short-term Load Forecasting for Distribution Network Using Decomposition with Ensemble prediction," in *2019 Chinese Automation Congress (CAC)*, Hangzhou, China, Aug. 2019, pp. 152–157, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CAC48633.2019.8997169>.
- [3] N. T. Dung and N. T. Phuong, "Short-Term Electric Load Forecasting Using Standardized Load Profile (SLP) And Support Vector Regression (SVR)," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 4548–4553, Aug. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2929>.
- [4] J. Zhu, H. Dong, W. Zheng, S. Li, Y. Huang, and L. Xi, "Review and prospect of data-driven techniques for load forecasting in integrated energy systems," *Applied Energy*, vol. 321, Sep. 2022, Art. no. 119269, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2022.119269>.
- [5] F. Dorado Rueda, J. Durán Suárez, and A. del Real Torres, "Short-Term Load Forecasting Using Encoder-Decoder WaveNet: Application to the French Grid," *Energies*, vol. 14, no. 9, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 2524, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14092524>.
- [6] D. Niu, Y. Wang, and D. D. Wu, "Power load forecasting using support vector machine and ant colony optimization," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 37, no. 3, pp. 2531–2539, Mar. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2009.08.019>.
- [7] G. F. Fan, Y. H. Guo, J. M. Zheng, and W. C. Hong, "Application of the Weighted K-Nearest Neighbor Algorithm for Short-Term Load Forecasting," *Energies*, vol. 12, no. 5, Jan. 2019, Art. no. 916, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en12050916>.
- [8] S. K. Filipova-Petrakieva and V. Dochev, "Short-Term Forecasting of Hourly Electricity Power Demand: Regression and Cluster Methods for Short-Term Prognosis," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 8374–8381, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4787>.
- [9] Y. Dong, Z. Zhang, and W. C. Hong, "A Hybrid Seasonal Mechanism with a Chaotic Cuckoo Search Algorithm with a Support Vector Regression Model for Electric Load Forecasting," *Energies*, vol. 11, no. 4, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en11041009>.
- [10] R. Zhang, Z. Y. Dong, Y. Xu, K. Meng, and K. P. Wong, "Short-term load forecasting of Australian National Electricity Market by an ensemble model of extreme learning machine," *IET Generation, Transmission & Distribution*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 391–397, 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1049/iet-gtd.2012.0541>.
- [11] M. Ghofrani, M. Ghayekhloo, A. Arabali, and A. Ghayekhloo, "A hybrid short-term load forecasting with a new input selection framework," *Energy*, vol. 81, pp. 777–786, Mar. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2015.01.028>.
- [12] W. Kong, Z. Y. Dong, Y. Jia, D. J. Hill, Y. Xu, and Y. Zhang, "Short-Term Residential Load Forecasting Based on LSTM Recurrent Neural Network," *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 841–851, Jan. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSG.2017.2753802>.
- [13] C. Tian, J. Ma, C. Zhang, and P. Zhan, "A Deep Neural Network Model for Short-Term Load Forecast Based on Long Short-Term Memory Network and Convolutional Neural Network," *Energies*, vol. 11, no. 12, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en11123493>.
- [14] L. Han, Y. Peng, Y. Li, B. Yong, Q. Zhou, and L. Shu, "Enhanced Deep Networks for Short-Term and Medium-Term Load Forecasting," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 4045–4055, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2888978>.
- [15] K. Park, S. Yoon, and E. Hwang, "Hybrid Load Forecasting for Mixed-Use Complex Based on the Characteristic Load Decomposition by Pilot Signals," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 12297–12306, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2892475>.
- [16] B. J. Chen, M. W. Chang, and C. J. Lin, "Load forecasting using support vector Machines: a study on EUNITE competition 2001," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 19, no. 4, pp. 1821–1830, Aug. 2004, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRS.2004.835679>.
- [17] J. Che and J. Wang, "Short-term load forecasting using a kernel-based support vector regression combination model," *Applied Energy*, vol. 132, pp. 602–609, Nov. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2014.07.064>.
- [18] J. Chakravorty, S. Shah, and H. N. Nagraja, "ANN and ANFIS for Short Term Load Forecasting," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 2818–2820, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1968>.
- [19] W. C. Hong, "Electric load forecasting by support vector model," *Applied Mathematical Modelling*, vol. 33, no. 5, pp. 2444–2454, May 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apm.2008.07.010>.
- [20] E. Ceperic, V. Ceperic, and A. Baric, "A Strategy for Short-Term Load Forecasting by Support Vector Regression Machines," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 28, no. 4, pp. 4356–4364, Aug. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRS.2013.2269803>.
- [21] A. Selakov, D. Cvijetinović, L. Milović, S. Mellon, and D. Bekut, "Hybrid PSO-SVM method for short-term load forecasting during periods with significant temperature variations in city of Burbank," *Applied Soft Computing*, vol. 16, pp. 80–88, Mar. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asoc.2013.12.001>.
- [22] W. Sun, "A Novel Hybrid GA Based SVM Short Term Load Forecasting Model," in *2009 Second International Symposium on Knowledge Acquisition and Modeling*, Wuhan, China, Aug. 2009, vol. 2, pp. 227–229, <https://doi.org/10.1109/KAM.2009.31>.
- [23] A. Kavousi-Fard, H. Samet, and F. Marzbani, "A new hybrid Modified Firefly Algorithm and Support Vector Regression model for accurate

- Short Term Load Forecasting," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 41, no. 13, pp. 6047–6056, Oct. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2014.03.053>.
- [24] M. Barman and N. B. Dev Choudhury, "Season specific approach for short-term load forecasting based on hybrid FA-SVM and similarity concept," *Energy*, vol. 174, pp. 886–896, May 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2019.03.010>.
- [25] M. Barman, N. B. Dev Choudhury, and S. Sutradhar, "A regional hybrid GOA-SVM model based on similar day approach for short-term load forecasting in Assam, India," *Energy*, vol. 145, pp. 710–720, Feb. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2017.12.156>.
- [26] H. Lu, M. Azimi, and T. Iseley, "Short-term load forecasting of urban gas using a hybrid model based on improved fruit fly optimization algorithm and support vector machine," *Energy Reports*, vol. 5, pp. 666–677, Nov. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2019.06.003>.
- [27] H. Jiang, Y. Zhang, E. Muljadi, J. J. Zhang, and D. W. Gao, "A Short-Term and High-Resolution Distribution System Load Forecasting Approach Using Support Vector Regression With Hybrid Parameters Optimization," *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 3341–3350, Jul. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSG.2016.2628061>.
- [28] X. Wang and Y. Wang, "A Hybrid Model of EMD and PSO-SVR for Short-Term Load Forecasting in Residential Quarters," *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, vol. 2016, Dec. 2016, Art. no. e9895639, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2016/9895639>.
- [29] Q. Chen, Y. Wu, X. Zhang, and X. Chen, "Forecasting system based on Wavelet Transform and PSO-SVM," in *Security and Identification 2008 2nd International Conference on Anti-counterfeiting*, Guiyang, China, Dec. 2008, pp. 305–309, <https://doi.org/10.1109/IWASID.2008.4688383>.
- [30] S. Qiang and Y. Pu, "Short-term power load forecasting based on support vector machine and particle swarm optimization," *Journal of Algorithms & Computational Technology*, vol. 13, Jan. 2019, Art. no. 1748301818797061, <https://doi.org/10.1177/1748301818797061>.
- [31] W. Sun and M. Ye, "Short-Term Load Forecasting Based on Wavelet Transform and Least Squares Support Vector Machine Optimized by Fruit Fly Optimization Algorithm," *Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 2015, Dec. 2015, Art. no. e862185, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2015/862185>.
- [32] Z. Guo, L. Hu, J. Wang, and M. Hou, "Short-term Load Forecasting Based on SSA-LSSVM Model," in *2021 4th International Conference on Energy, Electrical and Power Engineering (CEEPE)*, Chongqing, China, Apr. 2021, pp. 1215–1219, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CEEPE51765.2021.9475790>.
- [33] J. P. Liu and C. L. Li, "The Short-Term Power Load Forecasting Based on Sperm Whale Algorithm and Wavelet Least Square Support Vector Machine with DWT-IR for Feature Selection," *Sustainability*, vol. 9, no. 7, 2017, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su9071188>.

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Evaluation of Stock Closing Prices using Transformer Learning

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ABSTRACT

Predicting stock markets remains a critical and challenging task due to many factors, such as the enormous volume of generated price data, instant price data changes, and sensitivity to human sentiments, wars, and natural disasters. Since the previous three years of the COVID-19 pandemic, forecasting stock markets is more difficult, complex, and problematic for stock market analysts. However, technical analysts of the stock market and academic researchers are continuously trying to develop innovative and modern methods for forecasting stock market prices, using statistical techniques, machine learning, and deep learning-based algorithms. This study investigated a Transformer sequential-based approach to forecast the closing price for the next day. Ten sliding window timesteps were used to forecast next-day stock closing prices. This study aimed to investigate reliable techniques based on stock input features. The proposed Transformer-based method was compared with ARIMA, Long-Short Term Memory (LSTM), and Random Forest (RF) algorithms, showing its outstanding results on Yahoo Finance data, Facebook Intra data, and JPMorgan's Intra data. Each model was evaluated using Mean Absolute Error (MSE), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE).

Keywords-stock prediction; ARIMA; SARIMA; LSTM; transformer; stock volatility; stock market; stock market prediction; machine learning; deep learning

I. INTRODUCTION

The stock market has great potential for profitmaking [1]. Different techniques and studies have been presented to predict future prices, maximize the returns of investments, and minimize the corresponding risks [2]. However, there are still risks due to unpredictable fluctuations in stock market prices, complicated trading circumstances in practice [3], and the difficulty in interpreting price movement with domain knowledge. Various statistical techniques with good interpretation, such as auto-regressive [4], tree [5], and hidden Markov [6] models, have been introduced for this purpose. Powerful prediction models [7] are expensive to train but provide good results. The importance of deep learning models cannot be ignored in powerful prediction models for sequential data. Deep learning models are receiving more research interest due to the increasing number of available datasets, growing computational power, and long-term dependency capability [8-9]. Recurrent Neural Network (RNN)-based deep learning models such as RNN, LSTM, and Transformer have shown state-of-the-art results in time-series tasks. Analyzing historical stock market patterns can provide valuable insight in predicting stock values, optimizing gain, and minimizing losses [10-11]. Intercorrelation among different stocks is a crucial factor in estimating future stock prices. All tradable stocks in today's markets are interconnected through various attributes. Although correlation does not imply causation, strong Pearson's correlation scores suggest a potential relationship between correlated stocks. Therefore, investigating stock price

trends and forecasting future changes remains a popular research field.

This study aims to develop an advanced model for short-term price forecasting, considering factors such as the global economy, international politics, financial performance, stakeholder expectations, and financial reports. Traditional investors face difficulties in predicting market behavior and selecting effective forecasting techniques to maximize profits and minimize losses. Predicting future stock prices is a challenging task for investors, companies, and financial organizations [12]. Variables such as the national political environment, economic situation, and investor psychology are crucial to accurate predictions. Analysts in various fields face numerous challenges in the forecasting of financial markets [13]. Stock market predictions are heavily based on factors such as intrinsic value, financial performance, regulatory requirements, GDP, natural disasters, and other variables [14].

Machine learning algorithms have transformed stock market forecasting by leveraging large and nonlinear datasets. These methods have shown significant improvements over traditional approaches, ranging from 60% to 86% [15]. Long-term investment in established stocks is considered more profitable and requires less effort and time compared to other investments like bonds. However, short-term trading aims to capitalize on small fluctuations in stock values and requires substantial time and effort from traders, particularly when done manually. In this case, staying up-to-date with the latest stock

news is essential. Time-series stock market prediction models using statistical and machine learning methods help traders and investors make informed decisions based on historical data and market trends. However, these predictions are not always accurate, and investing in the stock market carries inherent risks. Traders and investors must employ well-informed strategies, risk management plans, and a deep understanding of the market to mitigate these risks. It is crucial to acknowledge that relying solely on stock market predictions does not guarantee success in trading or investing. By incorporating these considerations, investors can increase the likelihood of positive returns while minimizing the risk of loss. In light of the contributions of statistical, machine learning, and deep learning methods, this study aims to investigate two specific research questions:

RQ1: Do machine learning techniques outperform the statistical techniques when applied to time series data?

RQ2: Do deep learning models effectively address sequential data challenges and yield superior outcomes when compared to machine learning algorithms?

Previous studies used statistical time series methods such as moving averages and autoregressive techniques for stock market price forecasting. This study examined the efficacy of the Transformer deep learning model in predicting closing stock prices, leveraging its ability to handle long-term dependencies and address the vanishing gradient problem. This study aims to make the following contributions:

1. Present a novel Transformer-based framework for predicting stock prices of real indices, such as Yahoo, JPMorgan, and Facebook, using their intraday data.
2. Present a comparative analysis of random forest, LSTM, and Transformer-based models on three benchmark datasets.
3. Assess the prevalent machine and deep learning models that can benefit financial analysis.
4. Evaluate the effectiveness of proposed techniques using Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Mean Squared Error (MSE), and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE).

Machine learning and deep learning algorithms revolutionized stock forecasting using historical data. In [16], the influence between different machine learning algorithms and multi-feature methods in time series was studied. In [17], an algorithm was presented that combined artificial neural networks and genetic algorithms. In [18], a look-back period was used for accurate forecasting. In [19], an RNN was used with news data to achieve better performance than ARIMA. In [20], LSTM was used for growth calculation. In [21], the SARIMA and BPNN models were compared on the Korean stock exchange. Previous studies have shown that the SARIMA model outperforms the BPNN and KOSPI models. The KOSPI model excels at predicting volatile and nonlinear data. Prediction accuracy depends on the evolution of the model. In [22], regression techniques were used with ARIMA for stock market prediction. In [23], accurate stock price prediction was achieved in banking-related markets using ARIMA. In [24],

support vector machines, MLP, and logistic regression with technical indicators were used for NIFTY50 index prediction. In [25], a rigorous selection process was used to identify dynamic stocks on the Dar es Salaam Stock Exchange, using the LSTM and GRU deep learning models to forecast closing prices. The LSTM model outperformed GRU with a lower RMSE of 4.7524 and an MAE of 2.4377. In [26], a novel model was introduced combining LBL and RNN to capture short- and long-term sentiment patterns.

Deep learning algorithms are used in computer vision, video games, large data, and multimedia [27-28]. RNNs are commonly used for time series prediction due to their ability to capture past data [29-30]. In [31], Bayesian RNNs were implemented using variational inference and measuring the ambiguity of the prediction. CNNs are effective in forecasting time sequences, such as wind power [32] and precipitation [33] predictions. CNN and LSTM were combined in an ensemble approach for air pollution quality forecasting [34-35]. LSTM networks were used to predict river discharge levels [36], and forecast stock market trends [37-38]. CNNs were also suggested for market price forecasting [39]. The MFNN model [40] combined convolution and recursive neurons for feature extraction in fiscal time-series prediction. LSTM was also used to extract data and forecast stock values with improved performance [41]. Deep learning models have gained attention in various domains, including estimating future values. For example, in [42], a deep learning method was used to forecast short-term electricity demand.

II. METHODOLOGY

To achieve accurate and timely results in stock market forecasting, it is necessary to synchronize historical data with streaming data and train machine learning models accordingly. Numerous techniques have been proposed using machine learning for this purpose. This study used a regression-based model and an LSTM-based network model. Such models follow a specific structural design, as shown in Figure 1, which includes the following processes:

- Data Collection Stage: Stock data are collected to acquire the necessary dataset for analysis.
- Data Preprocessing Stage: The collected data are subjected to preprocessing techniques to be transformed into a suitable format for further analysis. This stage involves tasks such as data cleaning, handling missing values, and normalizing.
- Modeling Stage: At this stage, a stock forecast model is developed using the preprocessed data as input. Data analysis techniques are used to accurately predict the closing values of stocks.
- Performance Evaluation Stage: The model's results are evaluated by comparing them with the actual results to assess its validity. If the model fails to produce the desired results, further refinement of the model or data preprocessing techniques may be required. Otherwise, the results are presented to the user.

- Results Presentation Stage: In the final stage, the model and its predictions are visually presented to the user, allowing for a comprehensive understanding of the results.

Fig. 1. Time series data analysis flow.

A. Dataset

This study used three benchmark datasets: Yahoo's [43], Facebook's [44], and JPMorgan's [45] finance data, from January 1, 2017, to September 17. There were no identical or missing values in the dataset. Six features, common in all datasets, were used: High, Low, Open, Close, Noise, and Volume. The primary objective was to forecast the closing price based on past data. The dataset features are described as follows:

- Open price represents the initial price of a stock at the beginning of the market trading session.
- Close price signifies the final price of a stock when the market closes.
- High price indicates the highest value attained by a stock during a trading day.
- Low price denotes the lowest value reached by a stock during a trading day.
- Volume reflects the number of shares or trades executed for a particular stock within a given trading day.

Before conducting a comprehensive analysis and prediction of the closing price, the trends in the closing prices were examined, as shown in Figure 2. It was evident that during the initial phase of the COVID-19 pandemic, the closing prices of the stocks experienced a significant decline, reaching their lowest values.

Fig. 2. Closing price history.

B. Problem Statement

The multivariate time series X_t data at timestamp t were passed to the time series model. This was defined as follows:

$$X_t = \{X_{t-m+1}, X_{t-m+2}, X_{t-m+3}, \dots, X_t | X_i \in R^n\} \quad (1)$$

where m is the length of input multivariate time series data and X_t is the multivariate vector at timestamp t . A multivariate vector X_t contains n variables for a single time period. The n value depends on the attribute values of the dataset and can be expressed as follows:

$$X_t = \{X_{t(1)}, X_{t(2)}, X_{t(3)}, \dots, X_{t(n)} | X_i \in R \quad (2)$$

The multivariate time series input $X_t \in R^{(m \times n)}$ represents the historical multivariate data for a part-time period from $t-m+1$ to t . In this study, the dataset had multiple input variables to forecast the close prices based on past data. The approach was to predict the multivariate vector

$$X_{t+r} = \{x_{(t+r)(1)}, x_{(t+r)(2)}, \dots, x_{(t+r)(n)}\}$$

of timestamp $t+r$ with past historical data

$$X_t = \{X_{t-m+1}, X_{t-m+2}, \dots, X_t\}$$

as input.

C. Learning Based Approaches

1) Transformer

Although the Transformer architecture was originally designed for Natural Language Processing (NLP), this model has also found applications in time-series analysis and computer vision tasks. One of the key elements of Transformer is the attention mechanism, which allows for a targeted focus on specific information. This study used a variant called the sparse-attention Transformer to predict the closing prices of stocks. This variant offers reduced memory requirements, enabling effective handling of longer historical data for more accurate forecasting. Figure 3 illustrates the architecture of the proposed approach.

The Transformer distinguishes itself from previous approaches in time series data and forecasting by employing an attention mechanism [41]. This mechanism enables the Transformer to selectively focus on relevant information in historical data, disregarding irrelevant features. On the

contrary, LSTM encounters difficulties in processing long sequences of data due to short-term memory issues. LSTM updates a hidden state with each new input token, resulting in a prolonged sequence of input. However, LSTM encounters challenges in propagating the entire set of long input sequences due to the vanishing gradient problem. As a consequence, earlier tokens in the long input sequence are gradually forgotten. In contrast, Transformer retains indirect connections to all preceding timestamps, facilitating information propagation across significantly longer sequences.

Fig. 3. The Transformer architecture.

The Transformer model consists of two primary components, the encoder and the decoder. The encoder applies dot-product attention iteratively within the input sequence, preserving the sequence length. On the other hand, the decoder generates the output by using dot-product attention between the encoded input and output sequences, with the initial decoder layer containing a placeholder sequence. The proposed method used the full encoder-decoder structure, allowing the decoder to directly generate a forecast sequence of the desired length. The primary components of the Transformer model include the input, encoder, attention mechanism, and decoder.

- Input: The nonsequential processing of historical information poses a significant challenge for the Transformer network. To address this problem, positional encoding [47] is used to provide context on the relative distance between each token and the current timestamp. This information is crucial for determining relevance in the

self-attention mechanism. Positional encoding assigns a unique real number to each location, ensuring that it is not duplicated. The positional encoding function $PE(\cdot)$ for a given multivariate time series data X_i is illustrated in the following equations:

$$PE(x_i, 2k) = x_i + \sin\left(\frac{x_i}{10000^{\frac{2k}{d}}}\right) \quad (3)$$

$$PE(x_i, 2k + 1) = x_i + \cos\left(\frac{x_i}{10000^{\frac{2k}{d}}}\right) \quad (4)$$

The attention block calculates attention weights by taking the dot product between vectors. The size of the vectors determines the behavior of the attention mechanism. In this scenario, as the stock closing price is represented by a one-dimensional vector, this is addressed by expanding the input to a higher embedding dimension using a linear layer. The output of the linear layer transforms the decoder information into a one-dimensional sequence.

- Encoder: This is a layer that encompasses multiread self-attention along with a two-layer feedforward section.
- Attention: Dot product attention is a commonly used fusion mechanism within transformer models. It derives its name from the fact that attention weights are calculated through dot products of queries and key vectors. Self-attention is used in the encoder, expressed by the following equation [5]:

$$Attention(x) = \sigma\left(\frac{Q(X)(K(X))^T}{\sqrt{d}}\right)V(X) \quad (5)$$

This equation pertains to self-attention, wherein the query and key vectors are extracted from the input sequences. However, in the decoder attention block, the query vectors are obtained from the output sequence, while the key vectors are derived from the encoder output.

- Decoder: The decoder consists of multiple decoding layers, where each layer incorporates self-attention on the decoder output, and subsequently, attention is applied between the decoder output and the processed sequence obtained from the encoder.

2) Long Short-Term Memory Network (LSTM)

RNN is a variant of neural networks that incorporates feedback, allowing the modeling of sequential data. The LSTM model is a widely used RNN that excels in various problem domains [45-47]. LSTM units have a memory capability, enabling them to retain information from previous computations, making them suitable for tasks that involve sequential data. Within the LSTM model, gated cells play a pivotal role in regulating information flow within the network [48]. The LSTM architecture consists of input, forget, and output gates. The input gate (fi) controls the information to be updated based on the incoming signal, while the forget gate (ft) determines which states should be retained or forgotten. The output gate (Ot) decides whether the cell state should influence other neurons or not. Activation functions, such as logistic layers, produce values between 0 and 1 in each layer. The LSTM layer generates a new vector that is added to the state,

facilitating memory retention and information flow [49]. LSTM networks are useful for examining the impact of one stock's price change on multiple other stocks over time. They can provide insight into the duration for which past stock price patterns should be considered and help predict future trends in stock price variations. LSTM networks offer a powerful approach for analyzing time-series data and extracting meaningful insights for forecasting and trend analysis. The following equations provide a mathematical representation of the flow of information within LSTM:

$$f_t = \sigma(W_{xf}X_t + W_{yf}Y_{t-1} + b_f) \quad (6)$$

$$i_t = \sigma(W_{xi}X_t + W_{yi}Y_{t-1} + b_i) \quad (7)$$

$$g_t = \tanh(W_{xg}X_t + W_{yg}Y_{t-1} + b_g) \quad (8)$$

$$s_t = f_t * s_{t-1} + i_t * g_t \quad (9)$$

$$o_t = \sigma(W_{xo}X_t + W_{yo}Y_{t-1} + b_o) \quad (10)$$

$$y_t = o_t * \tanh(s_t) \quad (11)$$

The proposed LSTM model consists of an input layer, two hidden layers, and an output layer. The input layer consists of 50 neurons, while the first hidden layer consists of 50 neurons, and the second hidden layer contains 25 neurons. The final layer contains a single cell. The model was trained using two different group sizes, namely 1 and 15 epochs. This study used the Adam optimizer and MSE as the loss function. To determine the optimal parameters, a series of tests were conducted and the parameters that yielded the best results were selected.

3) Random Forest

This model is an ensemble approach that can assist in categorization and regression problems. While learning, a random selection of features is chosen using a modified tree-learning method. This approach regulates only a random subset of factors to determine the optimal split at each node. The input vector is given to each tree in the Random Forest Model (RFM) for the classification assignment, and each tree casts a vote for a class. Then, the class that receives the most scores is selected. Compared to other models, RFM can handle large input datasets and eliminates the overfitting problem by aggregating or combining the results of different decision trees. RFM is a suitable choice for time series tasks, due to its ensemble nature. This study used the random forest regressor with 100 estimators to predict the closing price. The RFM aggregates the outputs of individual decision trees to determine the mean value for regression tasks and uses consensus voting among decision trees for classification tasks. Several hyperparameters can be tuned to enhance the RFM performance. Notable hyperparameters include maximal features, minimal sample split, and the number of estimators. The number of estimators determines the number of decision trees constructed, and more trees generally improve performance at the cost of increasing computation time. The minimal sample split determines the minimum number of samples required to split an internal node, which should be adjusted based on the dataset's size. Furthermore, RFM is used to assess the relative importance of features, allowing the selection of the most significant

characteristics for model construction. Overall, the RFM provides a robust framework for tackling categorization and regression problems, particularly in handling large datasets and capturing temporal patterns.

III. RESULTS

Three benchmarks were used to train and testing the proposed models. These datasets were divided into training and test datasets in a 70:30 ratio, respectively. A PC with a 2.60 GHz Intel i7 CPU and 16 GB of RAM and Python Pytorch 4 on Widows 10 was used for all tests. The time (s) required to finish one round of processing is noted for each type. The following metrics were used, with their respective mathematical formulas:

- RMSE: Measures the deviation between the actual and predicted values.

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y' - y)^2} \quad (12)$$

- MAE: Represents the average of the absolute errors in prediction across all samples in the test dataset.

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y' - y| \quad (13)$$

- MAPE: Quantifies the accuracy of the predictions in percentage terms.

$$\text{MAPE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{|y' - y|}{y} \quad (14)$$

The investigation of RQ1 showed that machine learning algorithms yield superior outcomes compared to the statistical ARIMA model. This study used a range of models including ARIMA, Random Forest, LSTM, and Transformer. Tables I, II, and III display the comprehensive findings that correspond to the datasets collected from Yahoo Finance, Facebook, and JPMorgan, respectively. In particular, Tables I-III illustrate that the ARIMA model performed worse than the learning-based techniques. The investigation of RQ2 showed that deep learning algorithms delivered superior results compared to conventional machine learning models. This validation is evident in Tables I-III across all benchmark datasets. The RFM exhibited inferior performance when compared to LSTM and Transformer-based models. The Transformer-based approach demonstrated significantly improved results compared to both machine learning and statistical methods.

TABLE I. YAHOO FINANCE DATASET

Models	MAE	RMSE	MAPE
ARIMA	2.351	3.099	1.503
Random Forest	2.250	3.154	1.500
LSTM	1.758	2.157	1.425
Transformer	1.254	2.056	1.256

TABLE II. FACEBOOK STOCK FORECASTING RESULTS

Models	MAE	RMSE	MAPE
ARIMA	2.423	3.256	1.423
Random Forest	2.265	3.164	1.240
LSTM	1.756	2.124	1.435
Transformer	1.095	1.985	1.125

TABLE III. JPMORGAN FORECASTING RESULTS

Models	MAE	RMSE	MAPE
ARIMA	2.389	3.453	1.564
Random Forest	2.145	3.256	1.356
LSTM	1.0995	2.125	1.235
Transformer	1.088	1.865	1.116

Fig. 4. Transformer forecasting on (a) FB and (b) JP Morgan.

IV. DISCUSSION

Due to continuously fluctuating stock values that depend on numerous factors, predicting the return of the stock market is both important and difficult to do. This complexity and dependency on various factors make it difficult to accurately forecast the returns and closing prices of multiple stocks in the stock market. Although each company's website lists a small portion of the previous dataset, such as High, Low, Open, Close, and Volume, this information is inadequate to make a reliable forecast. This information only projects a narrow picture of the prospects and performance of the stock in the future. These variables can be used to generate new variables to increase the accuracy of the prediction. An increased number of variables responsible for the movement of the stock market can make the predictions more accurate. The most widely used method for making stock forecasts is a trend-based strategy that extrapolates a company's future worth from its historical stock prices. This method assumes that the particular company maintains its previous position and keeps going on the track, therefore, maintaining the projectile based on its past record. This is regarded as a tried-and-trusted strategy. Traders or investors have the greatest impact on a company's worth, and if everyone follows the same strategy, it will produce the same results. Since people tend to follow similar approaches, the result was expected. As a result, the primary driver of a company's ultimate value is its investors. Predicting broad trends is simple, but predicting a sudden shift in a company's worth is challenging and has long confounded academics and researchers, as it typically occurs as a result of various factors, such as significant company news or changes to the general stock market.

This study used an LSTM and a Transformer model to forecast stock market prices. These models were evaluated on three benchmark datasets, using three distinct situations, including daily predictions of using timestamps from 30, 60, and 90 days in the past. The results showed that a 90-day timeframe yielded superior results as the models advanced in their learning of more data distribution. The suggested techniques performed well, which can help achieve the desired outcomes. The combination of LSTM and regression significantly increased the precision of the process and

generated better outcomes. Newly developed deep learning techniques for market forecasting produced promising outcomes, as the proposed Transformed-based method maximized the accuracy of the predicted stock prices.

Due to the complications in examining the stock data and the fluctuating closing price of the stocks, it is difficult to carefully analyze the stock data using conventional machine learning methods. To decide which company's stock to purchase or sell, an investor must first understand how the stock market fluctuates. Future stock prices are heavily influenced by a variety of factors, including company traits, the stock's historical price, and recent financial news about that particular stock. This study was designed to assist investors in making informed decisions regarding the buy or sell process and protect them from potential financial losses.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE DIRECTION

The stock market is a complex and ever-changing environment that is difficult to predict accurately. Traditional methods of analyzing stock data may not be enough to provide investors with reliable insights into the stock market. Machine learning and deep learning algorithms offer promising solutions to this problem. By analyzing historical stock data and using advanced techniques, these algorithms can generate predictions with greater accuracy, enabling investors to make more informed decisions about buying or selling stocks. In addition, the Transformed-based framework proposed in this study could help investors protect themselves from financial loss by allowing them to predict the price of a stock and make more informed decisions. The proposed Transformer-based model has some limitations, such as input structure, temporal dependencies, interpretability, and limited training data. Stock exchange datasets have some time missing values and unstructured information that make the function and the results of the proposed model harder. Another problem is that time series are limited, so effective training cannot be possible. In the future, the ensemble approach of machine learning will be investigated with a bio-inspired technique to overcome these issues.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Thakkar and K. Chaudhari, "Fusion in stock market prediction: A decade survey on the necessity, recent developments, and potential future directions," *Information Fusion*, vol. 65, pp. 95–107, Jan. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inffus.2020.08.019>.
- [2] S. M. Idrees, M. A. Alam, and P. Agarwal, "A Prediction Approach for Stock Market Volatility Based on Time Series Data," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 17287–17298, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2895252>.
- [3] K. C. Rasekhschaffe and R. C. Jones, "Machine Learning for Stock Selection," *Financial Analysts Journal*, vol. 75, no. 3, pp. 70–88, Jul. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1080/0015198X.2019.1596678>.
- [4] C. S. Wong and W. K. Li, "On a Mixture Autoregressive Model," *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society Series B: Statistical Methodology*, vol. 62, no. 1, pp. 95–115, Jan. 2000, <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9868.00222>.
- [5] M. R. Hassan and B. Nath, "Stock market forecasting using hidden Markov model: a new approach," in *5th International Conference on Intelligent Systems Design and Applications (ISDA'05)*, Warsaw, Poland, Sep. 2005, pp. 192–196, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISDA.2005.85>.
- [6] E. K. Ampomah, Z. Qin, and G. Nyame, "Evaluation of Tree-Based Ensemble Machine Learning Models in Predicting Stock Price Direction

- of Movement," *Information*, vol. 11, no. 6, Jun. 2020, Art. no. 332, <https://doi.org/10.3390/info11060332>.
- [7] X. Yu and D. Li, "Important Trading Point Prediction Using a Hybrid Convolutional Recurrent Neural Network," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 11, no. 9, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 3984, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11093984>.
- [8] A. P. Ruiz, A. A. Gila, U. Irusta, and J. E. Huguet, "Why Deep Learning Performs Better than Classical Learning?," *DYNA Ingenieria e Industria*, vol. 95, no. 2, pp. 119–122, Mar. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.6036/9574>.
- [9] J. Liu, X. Guo, B. Li, and Y. Yuan, "COINet: Adaptive Segmentation with Co-Interactive Network for Autonomous Driving," in *2021 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*, Prague, Czech Republic, Sep. 2021, pp. 4800–4806, <https://doi.org/10.1109/IROS51168.2021.9636111>.
- [10] N. M. H. Masoud, "The Impact of Stock Market Performance upon Economic Growth," *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 788–798, Dec. 2013.
- [11] A. Murkute and T. Sarode, "Forecasting Market Price of Stock using Artificial Neural Network," *International Journal of Computer Applications*, vol. 124, no. 12, pp. 11–15, Aug. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.5120/ijca2015905681>.
- [12] L. J. Kao, C. C. Chiu, C. J. Lu, and J. L. Yang, "Integration of nonlinear independent component analysis and support vector regression for stock price forecasting," *Neurocomputing*, vol. 99, pp. 534–542, Jan. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neucom.2012.06.037>.
- [13] W. Khan, M. ali Ghazanfar, M. Assam, S. Ahmad, and J. Khan, "Predicting Trend in Stock Market Exchange Using Machine Learning Classifiers," *Science International*, vol. 28, no. 2, pp. 1363–1367, May 2016.
- [14] R. Gupta, N. Garg, and S. Singh, "Stock Market Prediction Accuracy Analysis Using Kappa Measure," in *2013 International Conference on Communication Systems and Network Technologies*, Gwalior, India, Apr. 2013, pp. 635–639, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CSNT.2013.136>.
- [15] A. E. Ezugwu *et al.*, "A comprehensive survey of clustering algorithms: State-of-the-art machine learning applications, taxonomy, challenges, and future research prospects," *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 110, Apr. 2022, Art. no. 104743, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2022.104743>.
- [16] L. Li, Y. Wu, Y. Ou, Q. Li, Y. Zhou, and D. Chen, "Research on machine learning algorithms and feature extraction for time series," in *2017 IEEE 28th Annual International Symposium on Personal, Indoor, and Mobile Radio Communications (PIMRC)*, Montreal, QC, Canada, Jul. 2017, pp. 1–5, <https://doi.org/10.1109/PIMRC.2017.8292668>.
- [17] J. Zhao, N. Sun, and W. Cheng, "Logistics forum based prediction on stock index using intelligent data analysis and processing of online web posts," *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*, vol. 11, no. 9, pp. 3575–3584, Sep. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12652-019-01520-x>.
- [18] A. S. Saud and S. Shakya, "Analysis of look back period for stock price prediction with RNN variants: A case study on banking sector of NEPSE," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 167, pp. 788–798, Jan. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2020.03.419>.
- [19] S. Mohan, S. Mullanpudi, S. Sammeta, P. Vijayvergia, and D. C. Anastasiu, "Stock Price Prediction Using News Sentiment Analysis," presented at the 2019 IEEE Fifth International Conference on Big Data Computing Service and Applications (BigDataService), Newark, CA, USA, Apr. 2019, pp. 205–208, <https://doi.org/10.1109/BigDataService.2019.00035>.
- [20] A. Ghosh, S. Bose, G. Maji, N. Debnath, and S. Sen, "Stock Price Prediction Using LSTM on Indian Share Market," in *Proceedings of 32nd International Conference on Computer Applications in Industry and Engineering*, 2019, pp. 101–110, <https://doi.org/10.29007/qgcz>.
- [21] "Neural Network Model vs. SARIMA Model In Forecasting Korean Stock Price Index (KOSPI)," *Issues In Information Systems*, vol. VIII, no. 2, 2007, https://doi.org/10.48009/2_iis_2007_372-378.
- [22] A. A. Ariyo, A. O. Adewumi, and C. K. Ayo, "Stock Price Prediction Using the ARIMA Model," in *2014 UKSim-AMSS 16th International Conference on Computer Modelling and Simulation*, Cambridge, UK, Mar. 2014, pp. 106–112, <https://doi.org/10.1109/UKSim.2014.67>.
- [23] M. Almasarweh and S. A. Wadi, "ARIMA Model in Predicting Banking Stock Market Data," *Modern Applied Science*, vol. 12, no. 11, 2018.
- [24] I. R. Parray, S. S. Khurana, M. Kumar, and A. A. Altalbe, "Time series data analysis of stock price movement using machine learning techniques," *Soft Computing*, vol. 24, no. 21, pp. 16509–16517, Nov. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00500-020-04957-x>.
- [25] S. Joseph, N. Mduma, and D. Nyambo, "A Deep Learning Model for Predicting Stock Prices in Tanzania," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 10517–10522, Apr. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5710>.
- [26] U. P. Gurav and S. Kotrappa, "Sentiment Aware Stock Price Forecasting using an SA-RNN-LBL Learning Model," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 6356–6361, Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3805>.
- [27] Y. LeCun, Y. Bengio, and G. Hinton, "Deep learning," *Nature*, vol. 521, no. 7553, pp. 436–444, May 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature14539>.
- [28] D. Salinas, V. Flunkert, J. Gasthaus, and T. Januschowski, "DeepAR: Probabilistic forecasting with autoregressive recurrent networks," *International Journal of Forecasting*, vol. 36, no. 3, pp. 1181–1191, Jul. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijforecast.2019.07.001>.
- [29] D. T. Mirikitani and N. Nikolaev, "Recursive Bayesian Recurrent Neural Networks for Time-Series Modeling," *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 262–274, Oct. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TNN.2009.2036174>.
- [30] H. Wang, G. Li, G. Wang, J. Peng, H. Jiang, and Y. Liu, "Deep learning based ensemble approach for probabilistic wind power forecasting," *Applied Energy*, vol. 188, pp. 56–70, Feb. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2016.11.111>.
- [31] X. Shi, Z. Chen, H. Wang, D.-Y. Yeung, W. Wong, and W. Woo, "Convolutional LSTM Network: A Machine Learning Approach for Precipitation Nowcasting," in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 2015, vol. 28.
- [32] K. Amarasinghe, D. L. Marino, and M. Manic, "Deep neural networks for energy load forecasting," in *2017 IEEE 26th International Symposium on Industrial Electronics (ISIE)*, Edinburgh, UK, Jun. 2017, pp. 1483–1488, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISIE.2017.8001465>.
- [33] C. J. Huang and P. H. Kuo, "A Deep CNN-LSTM Model for Particulate Matter (PM2.5) Forecasting in Smart Cities," *Sensors*, vol. 18, no. 7, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s18072220>.
- [34] Y. Sudriani, I. Ridwansyah, and H. A. Rustini, "Long short term memory (LSTM) recurrent neural network (RNN) for discharge level prediction and forecast in Cimandiri river, Indonesia," *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, vol. 299, no. 1, Apr. 2019, Art. no. 012037, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/299/1/012037>.
- [35] X. Ding, Y. Zhang, T. Liu, and J. Duan, "Deep learning for event-driven stock prediction," in *Proceedings of the 24th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, Buenos Aires, Argentina, Apr. 2015, pp. 2327–2333.
- [36] D. M. Q. Nelson, A. C. M. Pereira, and R. A. de Oliveira, "Stock market's price movement prediction with LSTM neural networks," in *2017 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)*, Anchorage, AK, USA, Feb. 2017, pp. 1419–1426, <https://doi.org/10.1109/IJCNN.2017.7966019>.
- [37] S. Al-Janabi, A. Alkaim, E. Al-Janabi, A. Aljeboree, and M. Mustafa, "Intelligent forecaster of concentrations (PM2.5, PM10, NO2, CO, O3, SO2) caused air pollution (IFCAsP)," *Neural Computing and Applications*, vol. 33, no. 21, pp. 14199–14229, Nov. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00521-021-06067-7>.
- [38] Y. Hu, "Stock market timing model based on convolutional neural network—a case study of Shanghai composite index," *Finance & Economy*, vol. 4, pp. 71–74, 2018.
- [39] W. Long, Z. Lu, and L. Cui, "Deep learning-based feature engineering for stock price movement prediction," *Knowledge-Based Systems*, vol. 164, pp. 163–173, Jan. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.knsys.2018.10.034>.
- [40] X. Pang, Y. Zhou, P. Wang, W. Lin, and V. Chang, "An innovative neural network approach for stock market prediction," *The Journal of*

- Supercomputing*, vol. 76, no. 3, pp. 2098–2118, Mar. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11227-017-2228-y>.
- [41] A. Zhang, Z. C. Lipton, M. Li, and A. J. Smola, "Dive into Deep Learning." arXiv, Feb. 10, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2106.11342>.
- [42] S. K. Filipova-Petrakieva and V. Dochev, "Short-Term Forecasting of Hourly Electricity Power Demand: Regression and Cluster Methods for Short-Term Prognosis," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 8374–8381, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4787>.
- [43] "Yahoo Finance - Stock Market Live, Quotes, Business & Finance News." <https://finance.yahoo.com/>.
- [44] "Meta - Financials." <https://investor.fb.com/financials/default.aspx>.
- [45] "J.P. Morgan Data and Analytics." <https://www.jpmorgan.com/securities-services/data-analytics>.
- [46] E. Haugsdal, E. Aune, and M. Ruocco, "Persistence Initialization: A novel adaptation of the Transformer architecture for Time Series Forecasting." arXiv, Aug. 30, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2208.14236>.
- [47] S. Hochreiter and J. Schmidhuber, "Long Short-Term Memory," *Neural Computation*, vol. 9, no. 8, pp. 1735–1780, Nov. 1997, <https://doi.org/10.1162/neco.1997.9.8.1735>.
- [48] S. Fernández, A. Graves, and J. Schmidhuber, "An Application of Recurrent Neural Networks to Discriminative Keyword Spotting," in *Artificial Neural Networks – ICANN 2007*, 2007, pp. 220–229, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-74695-9_23.
- [49] J. Schmidhuber, "Deep learning in neural networks: An overview," *Neural Networks*, vol. 61, pp. 85–117, Jan. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neunet.2014.09.003>.

Optimizing the Power System Operation Problem towards minimizing Generation and Damage Costs due to Load Shedding

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ABSTRACT

Optimizing the operational parameters and control of the power system in steady-state conditions is a crucial issue in reducing the costs of power generation and operation. In the case of long-term operation of a power system, besides aiming to minimize power generation costs, the cost of damage caused by load shedding also needs to be considered. This paper presents the optimization of the total cost of a power system including minimizing the generation cost function of power plants or power companies and minimizing the damage cost function caused to customers due to load shedding or power outages. At the same time, the objective function must also ensure the constraints on the operating conditions of the power system. This contributes to maintaining the continuity of the power supply to critical loads and minimizing damage. Base loads, priority loads, or loads that are not allowed to be shed are considered as constraints. The optimization problem is addressed by using the Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm and the Cuckoo Search Algorithm (CSA). The IEEE 30-bus test system is applied to validate the reduction in total cost. The result comparison shows that when applying the CSA, the total cost is significantly reduced by 3.75% in comparison with the PSO algorithm. The algorithms are implemented in Matlab to demonstrate the efficiency and accuracy of the proposed method.

Keywords-optimal load shedding; PSO; CSA; economic dispatch, cost function

I. INTRODUCTION

Maintaining the stable and continuous operation of a power system is a fundamental task that power system operators must ensure. In some cases, the power system cannot maintain its power balance due to prolonged generator failures or rapid increases in load beyond the generation capacity. At this time, shedding a portion of the load is the most effective solution if initial measures fail to restore power balance. Optimal load shedding has become an area of significant interest and development in power system operation optimization. In [1], an algorithm based on fuzzy logic that responds to load shedding

in order to provide an under-frequency load shedding scheme is introduced. Compared to the conventional load shedding solutions, the effectiveness of this method increases in the case of major disturbances and reduces in the case of small and medium failures. In [2], under-frequency load shedding is discussed with specific provisions for acceptable parameters, including the number of load shedding steps, the percentage of load shedding in each step, and the accuracy of the frequency measurement conducted in protective relays. Optimization techniques using algorithms such as Improved PSO (EPSO), Artificial Bee Colony PSO (ABC-PSO), Artificial Neural

Network-PSO (ANN-PSO), and Genetic Algorithm (GA) [3-5] are proposed to address under-voltage load shedding issues. These methods rely on the concept of voltage stability margin and its sensitivity at the maximum load ability point. The Grasshopper Optimization Algorithm (GOA) is employed to optimize frequency-responsive load shedding in [6], resulting in highly cost-effective load shedding solutions. Prominent artificial intelligence technologies such as ANNs, GAs, Fuzzy Logic Systems, etc., have been used to study effective and reliable load shedding measures [7-9]. These studies provide an overview of the above techniques when applied in the field of load shedding, aiming to highlight the advantages compared to the implementation of traditional techniques as well as the limitations when implementing. GA is used to design precise load shedding in [10]. The authors incorporated real-time decision-making to select appropriate load reduction levels for power system disturbances. However, the main disadvantage of GA is its slow response time. Higher effectiveness of load shedding was achieved by using the Chaotic Slime Mold Algorithm (CSMA) [10] with a sinusoidal diagram. It happens when constraints are imposed on the Voltage Stability Margin (VSM) and the total remaining load after shedding. Besides optimal load shedding, the operation optimization of power plants is also studied. Advanced algorithms such as PSO are applied to solve this problem in [12], and especially economic-environmental problems when optimally operating power plants in [13].

The above studies were evaluated as effective for individual objectives based on the specified problem statements. However, the comprehensive optimization of the overall cost of the entire power system has not been thoroughly examined. The objectives and constraints of this approach need further investigation and development. Therefore, this paper aims to apply the PSO and CSA optimization algorithms to find the optimal generation costs and minimize the costs associated with load shedding. To achieve the best efficiency in power generation operations for utility companies, the objective function for optimization is designed based on minimizing power generation costs with additional constraints. Furthermore, minimizing the cost of load shedding along with its associated constraints is considered a parallel objective. These constraints relate to the base loads or loads that are not allowed to be shed. In a competitive electricity market, optimizing all costs is crucial. The optimized cost includes power generation and load shedding costs while considering base load constraints, thus helping to decide whether load shedding should be implemented, and if so, how much power should be shed at different buses with varying consequential costs. As a result, the damage caused by load shedding is minimized, and the total cost is optimized.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

In this paper, the optimization problem consists of two parts as described in (1). The first part involves the generation cost of power plants $F_1(x)$ or the costs of the utility company during the considered period t . The second part encompasses the costs incurred $F_2(x)$ by customers due to power outages or load shedding.

$$\min F(x) = \min (F_1(x)t + F_2(x)) \quad (1)$$

where $F(x)$ is the total cost, including the generation cost and load shedding cost (\$), $F_1(x).t$ is a function of the generation cost for the period t (\$), and $F_2(x)$ is the cost function of the damage incurred by electricity consumers due to power cuts or load shedding (\$).

A. Minimizing the Generation Cost of Power Plants

The cost function of power plants, or the generation cost of the power company $F_1(x)$, is presented in (2):

$$\min F_1(x) = \min \sum_{i=1}^{N_G} (\alpha_i + \beta_i P_{Gi} + \gamma_i P_{Gi}^2) \quad (2)$$

where $F_1(x)$ is the generation cost function (\$/h), N_G is the total number of generators, including the slack bus, P_{Gi} is the active power output of the i^{th} generator (MW), and $\alpha_i, \beta_i, \gamma_i$ are the cost coefficients of the i^{th} generator.

B. Minimizing the Cost of Load Shedding

The cost function of the damage caused by load shedding is presented in (3):

$$\min F_2(x) = \min \sum_{j=1}^{NL} (P_{LS_j} C_j) \quad (3)$$

where P_{LS_j} is the amount of load shedding power at bus j (MW), and C_j is the cost of damage caused by load shedding at bus j (\$/MW).

C. Constraints of the Power System

When performing the optimization of functions $F_1(x)$ and $F_2(x)$, the constraints of the power system include equality and inequality constraints. This includes equations for balancing active and reactive power at the buses. In addition, the inequalities for the limits of apparent power, active power, reactive power, voltage, and phase angle at the buses are also considered when taking into account the constraints. In (2), the constraints include [14]:

$$f(x, y) = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$x^T = [P_{G_1}, V_{L_1} \dots V_{L_{NL}}, Q_{G_1} \dots Q_{G_{NL}}, S_{L_1} \dots S_{L_{NLT}}] \quad (5)$$

$$y^T = [V_{G_1} \dots V_{G_{NG}}, P_{G_2} \dots P_{G_{NG}}, T_1 \dots T_{NT}, Q_{c_1} \dots Q_{c_{NC}}] \quad (6)$$

where x is the vector of dependent variables consisting of the slack bus P_{G1} , load bus voltage V_L , generator reactive power output Q_G , and transmission line loading S_{Lj} , y is the vector of independent variables consisting of generator voltage V_G , generator active power output P_G except at the slack bus P_{G1} , transformer tap setting T , and shunt VAR compensation Q_c . NL, NG, NTL, NT , and NC are the number of load buses, generators, transmission lines, regulating transformers, and shunt compensators, respectively.

$$P_{gi}^{\min} \leq P_{Gi} \leq P_{gi}^{\max}, i = 1, \dots, NG \quad (7)$$

$$Q_{gi}^{\min} \leq Q_{Gi} \leq Q_{gi}^{\max}, i = 1, \dots, NG \quad (8)$$

$$V_{gi}^{\min} \leq V_i \leq V_{gi}^{\max}, i = 1, \dots, NG \quad (9)$$

$$V_{L_i}^{\min} \leq V_{L_i} \leq V_{L_i}^{\max}, i = 1, \dots, NL \quad (10)$$

$$S_{II} \leq S_{II,NTL}^{\max}, i = 1, \dots, NTL \quad (11)$$

$$\delta_{gi}^{\min} \leq \delta_i \leq \delta_{gi}^{\max}, i = 1, NG \quad (12)$$

$$T_i^{\min} \leq T_i \leq T_i^{\max}, i = 1, \dots, NTL \quad (13)$$

$$Q_{c_i}^{\min} \leq Q_{c_i} \leq Q_{c_i}^{\max}, i = 1, \dots, NC \quad (14)$$

In (3), the constraints include:

The total load shedding power at load buses P_{LSj} must be equal to the total required load shedding power for the entire system P_{LS} .

$$\sum_{j=1}^{NL} P_{LSj} = P_{LS} \quad (15)$$

The load shedding power at load buses must not exceed the allowable limit and maintain the base load $P_{base,j}$. A base load is a load that does not allow to be shed and must remain in the power system.

$$P_{L_j, \min} \leq P_{LSj} \leq P_{L_j, \max} \quad (16)$$

$$P_{base,j} = P_{L_j} - P_{L_j, \max} \quad (17)$$

III. PSO AND CSA

A. PSO

The PSO algorithm [15] is a widely used method for solving optimization problems in power system operation [16]. In PSO, each individual in the swarm is represented as a vector. These vectors move towards a position in a multi-dimensional search space. Each individual also remembers its own best historical position, called P_{best} . For each iteration of the PSO algorithm, the best global position G_{best} , is found. Once G_{best} is found, each individual will move closer to its own best position and the global best position. After many iterations, this process finds a good network structure for the objective function. The positions of the individuals during the convergence process of the PSO algorithm are presented in Figure 1. The velocity and position of each individual are described by (18):

$$V_i^{k+1} = w.V_i^k + c_1.r_1.(P_{best_i} - x_i^k) + c_2.r_2.(G_{best} - x_i^k) \quad (18)$$

After each iteration, the position of each individual will be updated according to (19):

$$x_i^{k+1} = x_i + V_i^{k+1} \quad (19)$$

where w is the inertia weight function, i is the iteration step, c_1 and c_2 are the acceleration coefficients, r_1 and r_2 are randomly generated numbers within the range of $[0, 1]$, V_i^k is the velocity of an individual, and x_i is the current position of the same individual.

B. CSA

The CSA [17] is based on the survival behavior of cuckoo birds. The algorithm's solution update equation is:

$$X_i^{new} = Xbest_i + a \oplus Levy \text{ flights} \quad (20)$$

where X_i is the solution of the i^{th} individual, $Xbest_i$ is the solution of the i^{th} individual from the previous iteration, p_α is the probability parameter for a random walk, $a > 0$ is the step size parameter. The product \oplus means entry-wise multiplications. This entry-wise product is similar to those used in PSO, but here the random walk via Lévy flights is more efficient in exploring the search space as its step length is much longer in the long run. The quantity of accessible host nests remains constant, and a host bird detects a cuckoo's laid egg with a probability $p_\alpha \in [0,1]$. In such instances, the host bird has the option to either discard the egg or forsake the nest entirely, constructing an entirely new nest. To simplify, this latter assumption can be approximated by the proportion p_α of the total nests being substituted with new nests (containing new, random solutions).

Fig. 1. The positions of the individuals during the convergence process of the PSO algorithm.

IV. SIMULATION AND RESULTS

The IEEE 30-bus test system is utilized to test the effectiveness of the proposed technique. This system includes 6 generators, 21 loads, and 41 transmission lines. The single-line diagram of the system is shown in Figure 2. The detailed parameters of the diagram are presented in [18]. In the case study, the IEEE-30 bus system has a load profile as shown in Figure 3. The load parameters for different time intervals t are presented in Table I and Figure 3. There are two times when the system is overloaded, and the total generated power value cannot meet the load demand at times t_3 (8:01 h ÷ 12:00 h) and t_5 (16:01 h ÷ 20:00 h). The power needs to be shed at t_3 and t_5 are 20.87 MW and 50.05 MW. The optimization of the generation cost function $F_1(x)$ using the PSO algorithm has been calculated and presented in [18]. The results of the cost coefficient values $\alpha_i, \beta_i, \gamma_i$ and the optimal generation power values P_{Gi} are shown in Table II. The cost function of load shedding damage $F_2(x)$ is applied when the system has to perform load shedding. In this case study, the generators have generated power according to the optimal result of the function $F_1(x)$. However, the total generated power cannot meet the load

demand. At times t_3 and t_5 , the system must perform load shedding with a power of P_{LS,t_3} being 20.87 MW, and P_{LS,t_5} being 50.05 MW. To achieve the minimum value of the function $F_2(x)$, corresponding to the amount of power shed at each load bus must be the optimal value, the PSO and CSA are continued to be used to solve this optimization problem. As a result, the load shedding cost function achieves its lowest. Solving the economic optimization problem of load shedding costs reduces the damage to customers due to power outages.

Fig. 2. The diagram of the IEEE-30 bus power system.

In this paper, the base load is proposed as a constraint parameter that must be complied with. The value of load shedding power must not exceed this base load limit. In this case, the value of the base load that needs to be maintained is 20% of the load value at bus j . The results in Table III show

that the operating costs of the power plants at t_3 and t_5 are the same, with a value of \$3144.12. However, the load shedding costs at each time interval t have different values. At t_5 , the PSO algorithm optimizes the objective function $F_2(x)$ for a cost value of $\$13488.28 \times 10^3$, corresponding to a load shedding power of 50.40 MW. On the other hand, if the objective function $F_2(x)$ is optimized using the CSA, the cost value is $\$13000.85 \times 10^3$, corresponding to a load shedding power of 50.45 MW. The calculation of total cost shows that the CSA reduces \$487427.6 (i.e. 3.75%) the damage cost due to load shedding. This cost reduction is very significant in the system. The CSA has better performance than the PSO algorithm because the CSA uses Lévy flights to generate new solutions. This increases the ability to produce diverse solutions and facilitates finding better optimal solutions easily. The convergence characteristics of the PSO and CSA are presented in Figure 4.

Fig. 3. Load profile versus time for the IEEE 30-bus system.

TABLE I. LOAD PARAMETERS AND COSTS OF LOAD SHEDDING OVER TIME

Name of Bus	C_j (\$/kW)	Load t_1 (MW) (0.00h-4.00h)	Load t_2 (MW) (4.01h-8.00h)	Load t_3 (MW) (8.01h-12.00h)	Load t_4 (MW) (12.01h-16.00h)	Load t_5 (MW) (16.01h-20.00h)	Load t_6 (MW) (20.01h-24.00h)
Claytor	300	19.18	19.18	22.9	19.18	23.48	19.18
Kumis	300	5.92	5.92	3.9	5.92	6.38	5.92
Hancock	300	9.49	9.49	9	9.49	10.81	9.49
Fieldale	280	69.97	69.97	95.4	69.97	88.73	69.97
Blaine	280	19.99	19.99	24	19.99	24.47	19.99
Reusens	300	25.03	25.03	31.2	25.03	30.95	25.03
Roanoke	300	8.09	8.09	7	8.09	9.17	8.09
Hancock	280	11.87	11.87	12.4	11.87	14.03	11.87
Bus 14	280	8.37	8.37	7.4	8.37	9.53	8.37
Bus 15	245	9.77	9.77	9.4	9.77	11.33	9.77
Bus 16	220	6.48	6.48	4.7	6.48	7.1	6.48
Bus 17	280	10.33	10.33	10.2	10.33	12.05	10.33
Bus 18	220	6.27	6.27	4.4	6.27	6.77	6.27
Bus 19	245	10.68	10.68	10.7	10.68	12.6	10.68
Bus 20	280	5.57	5.57	3.4	5.57	5.93	5.57
Bus 21	280	16.28	16.28	18.7	16.28	19.7	16.28
Bus 23	220	6.27	6.27	4.4	6.27	6.77	6.27
Bus 24	220	10.12	10.12	9.9	10.12	11.78	10.12
Bus 26	300	6.48	6.48	4.7	6.48	7.1	6.48
Bus 29	220	5.71	5.71	3.6	5.71	6.11	5.71
Bus 30	245	11.45	11.45	11.8	11.45	13.49	11.45
Total		283.4	283.4	309.1	283.4	338.28	283.4

Fig. 4. The convergence characteristics of PSO and CSA algorithms at time intervals t_3 and t_5 .

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, PSO and CSA have been applied to solve the multi-objective problem in optimizing generation cost and minimizing damages cost caused by load shedding. In the

problem of optimizing the cost function of load shedding, the CSA optimizes the damage cost function effectively.

TABLE II. OPTIMAL GENERATION POWER P_{Gi} VALUES AND THE CORRESPONDING COST COEFFICIENTS WHEN USING THE PSO ALGORITHM

Control variables	α_i	β_i	γ_i	PSO
P_{G1} (MW)	0	200	37.5	189.12
P_{G2} (MW)	0	175	175	47.55
P_{G3} (MW)	0	100	625	19.56
P_{G4} (MW)	0	325	83	10.00
P_{G5} (MW)	0	300	25	10.00
P_{G6} (MW)	0	300	250	12.00
Fuel cost (\$/h)				786.03

The achieved value using this method is \$487427.6, showing a reduction of 3.75% compared to the PSO algorithm. This reduction in damage cost is crucial in the competitive electricity market. The proposed method has addressed the overall optimization problem, including optimizing power generation and the damage due to power outage. In addition, load shedding takes into account the base load or the maximum allowable load shedding. This helps maintain critical loads in the electricity market. The CSA uses Lévy flight to increase discovery in search and performs a second check after each iteration. However, in this paper, only two algorithms were used for comparison. The proposed method opens up new research directions in applying advanced algorithms to solve the overall optimization problem considering multi-objective constraints and base load to be maintained.

TABLE III. LOAD SHEDDING POWER AT EACH LOAD BUS WHEN APPLYING PSO AND CSA

Name of Bus	t_3 (8.01h – 12h)			t_5 (16.01h – 20h)		
	P_{LS_j} (PSO)	P_{LS_j} (CSA)	$P_{LS_j,max}$	P_{LS_j} (PSO)	P_{LS_j} (CSA)	$P_{LS_j,max}$
Claytor	1.59	0.01	18.32	1.17	0.62	18.78
Kumis	1.64	0.26	3.12	3.36	0.16	5.10
Hancock	1.56	0.03	7.2	0.88	1.39	8.64
Fieldale	0.01	1.69	76.32	1.49	13.26	70.98
Blaine	0.82	0.00	19.2	1.50	0.01	19.57
Reusens	1.63	0.01	24.96	5.29	0.01	24.76
Roanoke	0.46	0.01	5.6	4.45	0.03	7.33
Hancock	1.46	0.81	9.92	0.19	3.03	11.22
Bus 14	0.40	4.27	5.92	4.40	0.00	7.62
Bus 15	0.72	0.67	7.52	2.44	0.01	9.06
Bus 16	0.64	0.00	3.76	0.52	1.98	5.68
Bus 17	0.85	4.19	8.16	1.11	0.11	9.64
Bus 18	2.10	2.38	3.52	3.79	0.01	5.41
Bus 19	1.99	0.00	8.56	0.28	12.81	10.08
Bus 20	0.43	3.76	2.72	2.25	2.23	4.74
Bus 21	0.63	0.00	14.96	4.19	0.00	15.76
Bus 23	0.54	0.32	3.52	3.53	0.01	5.41
Bus 24	1.36	1.11	7.92	1.55	4.51	9.42
Bus 26	0.50	0.00	3.76	2.42	3.58	5.68
Bus 29	0.76	0.03	2.88	4.77	6.70	4.88
Bus 30	0.84	1.33	9.44	0.82	0.00	10.79
Total load shedding (MW)	20.91	20.88		50.40	50.45	
CPU time (s)	42.76	4.58		23.46	2.67	
Load shedding cost: $F_2(x) = \sum_{j=1}^{NL} (P_{LS_j} C_j) (\times 10^3 \$)$	5555.59	5551.21		13488.28	13000.85	
Generation cost: $F_1(x)_t$ (\$)	3144.12	3144.12		3144.12	3144.12	
Total cost: $F(x) = (F_1(x)_t + F_2(x)) (\times 10^3 \$)$	5558.74	5554.35		13491.42	13000.4	
Save cost: $\Delta F(x)$ (\$)	4382.54			487427.60		

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REFERENCES

- [1] R. Małkowski and J. Nieznański, "Underfrequency Load Shedding: An Innovative Algorithm Based on Fuzzy Logic," *Energies*, vol. 13, no. 6, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 1456, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13061456>.
- [2] B. Potel, V. Debusschere, F. Cadoux, and L. de Alvaro Garcia, "Under-frequency load shedding schemes characteristics and performance criteria," in *2017 IEEE Manchester PowerTech*, Manchester, UK, Jun. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1109/PTC.2017.7981046>.
- [3] S. M. Kisengeu, C. M. Muriithi, and G. N. Nyakoe, "Under voltage load shedding using hybrid ABC-PSO algorithm for voltage stability enhancement," *Heliyon*, vol. 7, no. 10, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e08138>.
- [4] M. Usman, A. Amin, M. M. Azam, and H. Mokhlis, "Optimal under voltage load shedding scheme for a distribution network using EPSO algorithm," in *2018 1st International Conference on Power, Energy and Smart Grid (ICPESG)*, Mirpur Azad Kashmir, Pakistan, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICPESG.2018.8384525>.
- [5] M. A. Zdiri, A. S. Alshammari, A. A. Alzamil, M. B. Ammar, and H. H. Abdallah, "Optimal Shedding Against Voltage Collapse Based on Genetic Algorithm," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7695–7701, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4448>.
- [6] M. Talaat, A. Y. Hatata, A. S. Alsayyari, and A. Alblawi, "A smart load management system based on the grasshopper optimization algorithm using the under-frequency load shedding approach," *Energy*, vol. 190, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 116423, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2019.116423>.
- [7] L. T. H. Nhung, T. T. Phung, H. M. V. Nguyen, T. N. Le, T. A. Nguyen, and T. D. Vo, "Load Shedding in Microgrids with Dual Neural Networks and AHP Algorithm," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 8090–8095, Feb. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4652>.
- [8] M. Moazzami, A. Khodabakhshian, and R.-A. Hooshmand, "A New Optimal Under-frequency Load-shedding Method Using Hybrid Culture-Particle Swarm Optimization-Co-evolutionary Algorithm and Artificial Neural Networks," *Electric Power Components and Systems*, vol. 43, no. 1, pp. 69–82, Jan. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1080/15325008.2014.963264>.
- [9] T. N. Le, H. A. Quyen, and N. A. Nguyen, "Application of fuzzy-analytic hierarchy process algorithm and fuzzy load profile for load shedding in power systems," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 77, pp. 178–184, May 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijepes.2015.11.044>.
- [10] M. E. Jabian, R. Funaki, and J. Murata, "Load Shedding Optimization Considering Consumer Appliance Prioritization Using Genetic Algorithm for Real-time Application," *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, vol. 51, no. 28, pp. 486–491, Jan. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ifacol.2018.11.750>.
- [11] Md. S. Abid, H. J. Apon, A. Ahmed, and K. A. Morshed, "Chaotic slime mould optimization algorithm for optimal load-shedding in distribution system," *Ain Shams Engineering Journal*, vol. 13, no. 4, p. 101659, Jun. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asej.2021.101659>.
- [12] G. A. Alshammari, F. A. Alshammari, T. Guesmi, B. M. Alshammari, A. S. Alshammari, and N. A. Alshammari, "A New Particle Swarm Optimization Based Strategy for the Economic Emission Dispatch Problem Including Wind Energy Sources," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7585–7590, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4279>.
- [13] T. Dridi, H. Jouini, A. Mami, A. E. Mhamedi, and E. M. Dafaoui, "Application of the Levenberg-Marquardt Algorithm in Solving the Economic Emission Dispatch Problem Integrating Renewable Energy," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 8850–8855, Aug. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5002>.
- [14] M. A. Abido, "Optimal power flow using particle swarm optimization," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 24, no. 7, pp. 563–571, Oct. 2002, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0142-0615\(01\)00067-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0142-0615(01)00067-9).
- [15] R. C. Eberhart, Y. Shi, and J. Kennedy, *Swarm Intelligence*, 1st ed. San Francisco, CA, USA: Morgan Kaufmann, 2001.
- [16] D. Wang, D. Tan, and L. Liu, "Particle swarm optimization algorithm: an overview," *Soft Computing*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 387–408, Jan. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00500-016-2474-6>.
- [17] X.-S. Yang and S. Deb, "Cuckoo Search via Lévy flights," in *2009 World Congress on Nature & Biologically Inspired Computing (NaBIC)*, Coimbatore, India, Sep. 2009, pp. 210–214, <https://doi.org/10.1109/NABIC.2009.5393690>.
- [18] S. A. Mohamed, N. Anwer, and M. M. Mahmoud, "Solving optimal power flow problem for IEEE-30 bus system using a developed particle swarm optimization method: towards fuel cost minimization," *International Journal of Modelling and Simulation*, Apr. 2023, Art. no. 2201043, <https://doi.org/10.1080/02286203.2023.2201043>.

Fault Diagnosis of Rotating Machinery based on the Minutiae Algorithm

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ABSTRACT

Rotary machinery plays an important role in industry. Combined faults can be observed in rotating machinery, making fault classification difficult. In this paper, the Minutiae algorithm is used to classify the faults from the frequency domain of a particular fault. This paper provides a fault classification technique based on image processing for fault analysis of rotating machinery, recognizing function extraction automatically. Minutiae algorithm, a rising method within the discipline of image processing for characteristic extraction, is utilized in this paper to classify specific faults from the converted recurrence plot. The results reveal the effectiveness of the proposed method, providing a rather powerful tool for fault diagnosis of rotating machinery. The proposed model achieved an accuracy of 100% for combined faults, 98.33% for loosened faults, and 95% for unbalanced faults proving its applicability.

Keywords-rotating machinery; fault diagnosis; Minutiae algorithm

I. INTRODUCTION

Rotary machines, also known as rotor bearing systems, play an important role in industry. With the rapid development of science and technology, critical machines in industry are becoming faster and more complex. Critical and essential machines are machines that have high capital costs, require high or moderate costs to repair, take more time, and require skilled personnel. In addition, the unexpected shutdown or failure of critical and essential machinery affects plant safety and causes significant production losses. Therefore, accurate and reliable diagnosis of critical and important machine faults is of utmost importance. In this concern, single and multiple fault diagnostics of rotating machines have become important among researchers and operators. Condition monitoring and failure diagnostics of rotating machines are extremely important for the safety and reliability of industrial production [1]. During the recent decades, many signal processing techniques, such as symplectic geometry mode decomposition [2], variational mode decomposition [3], neural network and wavelet transform [4], wavelet packet decomposition, Fourier transform, artificial neural networks [5], and empirical wavelet transform and fuzzy entropy [6], have been widely used to analyze the nonlinear and nonstationary signals. Authors in [7] used BP-ANN for the identification of bearing cap looseness with an overall success

rate of 90%. Authors in [4] successfully predicted the effects of unbalance and shaft bow combined faults on the frequency components of the FFT spectrum of rotating machinery using ANN and Wavelet Transform (WT). Their method was successfully tested for single and combined unbalance and shaft bow. Authors in [8] developed a finite element model of a rotor system with a loose pedestal, and they examined the effects of pedestal displacement and looseness clearance on the system dynamic properties. Authors in [9] employed ANNs to detect pedestal looseness and imbalance in the rotor bearing system. Their findings demonstrated that statistical characteristics gave better results than frequency domain. Authors in [10] used a combined time series analysis algorithm and ANNs to detect and diagnose the fault. Authors in [11] used time series analysis and ANNs for fault diagnosis of rotating machinery. Authors in [12] divided vibration signals into many product functions using the local mean decomposition method, and then they calculated the multi-scale entropy of each product function as feature vectors. These feature vectors subsequently served as the input for the fault classifier, which completes the fault classification. All these technologies, however, primarily rely on 1-dimensional vibration signal processing methods. Authors in [13] proposed an effective fault diagnosis method based on Multi-Scale Dimensionless Indicator (MSDI) and random forests. They reported that their approach can accurately identify various fault

types with an average precision of 95.58%. Authors in [14] used Support Vector Machine (SVM), ANNs, and k-Nearest Neighbor (kNN) for fault diagnosis of rotating machinery. Different vibration signals may be categorized based on the extracted characteristics using various classification techniques, including Logistic Regression (LR), SVMs, and ANNs [15]. Authors in [16] used FFT of IMFs from the Hilbert-Huang Transform process to utilize the efficiency of Hilbert Transform in the frequency domain. Authors in [17] utilized a SVM with a Genetic Algorithm (GA) to diagnose a power transformer fault, with the GA being used to choose the proper SVM free parameters. Authors in [18] used amino acid sequences to address challenges with the categorization of macromolecules using deep learning models such as Convolution Neural Networks (CNNs), LSTM, and Gated Recurrent Units (GRU). Authors in [19] used a neural network-based model to classify the state of the gearbox into good (unbroken tooth) condition and poor (broken tooth). They claimed that BLSTM accuracy with an incomplete autoencoder is extremely reliable and suitable for time series data-based health monitoring of wind turbine gearbox systems. Authors in [20] studied metallic clutch damper springs included in the 1-D modeling of the powertrain system that was subjected to vibration optimization using the Simulated Annealing (SA) technique. This cutting-edge technology expedites the optimization of the engine system's vibration and offers presumptions that save money and time during actual vehicle testing.

The Minutiae algorithm approach is recognized as an attractive descriptor for practical usage and for matching features with strong resilience and high accuracy due to the advancement of the image automated feature extraction technology during the recent decades. It is used in this study to extract defect characteristics from recursive graphs. Once the Minutiae features are extracted, they can be used for fault classification and pattern recognition. By comparing the extracted patterns with known fault signatures, the algorithm can identify the type and severity of the fault. The effectiveness of the suggested method is tested through the use of fault diagnosis cases, such as unbalanced, loosened, and combined fault.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Experimental Setup

The tests were conducted on the test rig shown in Figure 1. The test-rig consists of a shaft of 25 mm diameter and 700 mm length which is supported on two double row deep groove ball bearings (SKF1205). At the midpoint of the bearings, a single 130 mm-diameter, 18 mm-thick rotor disc is mounted. Eight evenly distributed 12 mm diameter holes with a 45 mm radius are present on the rotor disc, which can be used to produce unbalance by adding weight. A 1 hp DC motor drives the rotor, and a DC controller regulates its speed. The rigid flange coupling is used to connect the rotor shaft (driven shaft) and motor shaft (driving shaft). The parallel misalignment of 0.2 mm in vertical direction was created in coupling by placing shims below DE and NDE bearings housing. Pedestal looseness is obtained by loosening the pedestal bolts. The rotor operating speed was kept at 1000 rev/min.

Fig. 1. The rotor test rig.

Fig. 2. The FFT analyzer.

A four channel FFT analyzer (Make: Adash; Model: VA4Pro) is used to measure and analyze the vibrations (Figure 2). The vibration signals in the Horizontal (H), Vertical (V), and Axial (A) direction at a bearing-housing are collected using three piezoelectric accelerometers (Make: CTC; Model: AC102-1A) with 100 mV/g sensitivity. The data acquisition parameters are given in Table I. The frequency spectra of unbalanced (Figure 3), loosened (Figure 4), and combined (Figure 5) faults were obtained. Figure 3 shows one peak and Figure 4 shows two peaks higher than the others. In Figure 5, multiple peaks are observed. A total of 60 testing signals of unbalanced, loosened and combined faults were obtained under our experimental conditions.

TABLE I. DATA ACQUISITION PARAMETERS

Sampling Frequency	4096 Hz
No. of Samples	4096
Window	Hanning
No. of lines	1600
Frequency range	10 Hz -1600 Hz
Time	1 s

Fig. 3. Frequency spectrum of unbalanced fault.

Fig. 4. Frequency spectrum of loosened fault.

Fig. 5. Frequency spectrum of combined fault.

B. The Minutiae Algorithm

Minutiae algorithms can be adapted to various types of machinery and different kinds of sensor data, making them versatile tools for fault diagnosis in a wide range of industrial applications. Minutiae algorithms enable data-driven decision making, where maintenance actions are based on the analysis of actual machine performance data rather than predetermined schedules. This approach, known as predictive maintenance, optimizes maintenance efforts and reduces unnecessary downtime. The flow chart of the fault diagnostic system with the use of the Minutiae Algorithm is shown in Figure 6. The steps of the followed method are:

Represent the mechanical system as a graph: Each node in the graph represents a component of the system, and each edge represents a connection or interaction between two components.

Define the rotating faults to be detected: For example, faults such as misaligned gears or bearings, unbalanced loads, or irregular vibrations.

Extract features from the graph: Graph analysis techniques can be used to extract various features from the graph, such as node degree, betweenness centrality, and clustering coefficient. These features can capture different aspects of the graph's structure and dynamics.

Application of the Minutiae algorithm: Compare the extracted features from the graph at different time points to

identify any small, unique features that are indicative of the rotating faults defined in step 2.

Train a machine learning model: Use the identified features as input to a machine learning model that can learn to detect the rotating faults automatically. You can train the model using labelled data, where you have examples of the system both with and without the faults.

In image processing, morphological operations are used to analyze and manipulate the shapes and structures within an image. These operations are typically applied to binary images and involve the use of a structuring element, which defines the neighborhood around each pixel. The function `cv2.getStructuringElement()` is used to create a structuring element of a specific shape and size. In this case, `cv2.MORPH_ELLIPSE` is used as the shape argument (equation for getting the kernel: `cv2.getStructuringElement(cv2.MORPH_ELLIPSE, (3, 3))`). The size of the structuring element is specified as (3, 3), indicating a 3x3 matrix. The resulting kernel variable represents the generated structuring element and can be used in various morphological operations, such as erosion, dilation, opening, and closing, to modify and enhance the shape and structure of the image.

$$\text{Element} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \left(\frac{x-1}{1.5}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{y-1}{1.5}\right)^2 \leq 1 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Morphological operations in image processing involve the manipulation of shapes and structures within an image. These operations are commonly used for tasks such as noise removal, feature extraction, and image enhancement. In this specific code snippet, the `dilation()` function is applied to the `input_image` using the kernel structuring element. This operation expands or enlarges the regions in the image based on shape and size defined by the kernel. The resulting image is stored in the `output_image` variable. Dilation is used to enhance or enlarge features, fill in gaps, and fuse nearby structures:

$$\text{dilation}(I, B)(x, y) = \max \{ I(x-i, y-j) : b(i, j) = 1 \}$$

where (x, y) represents a pixel position in the output dilated image, and (x-i, y-j) represents the corresponding pixel positions in the input image I based on the structuring element B.

Next, the `erosion()` function is applied to the `output_image` using the same kernel structuring element. Erosion is a fundamental morphological operation in image processing that aims to shrink or erode the regions of an image based on the shape and size defined by the structuring element. It is used to remove small details, smooth the boundaries, and separate overlapping structures. This operation removes or shrinks the regions in the image, complementing the previous dilation operation. The resulting image after erosion is not stored in a separate variable, but the operation is directly applied to the `output_image` itself. The combined effect of dilation followed by erosion is known as the opening operation. It helps to smooth out the image, remove small isolated regions, and refine the boundaries of objects in the image.

Fig. 6. Flow chart of the fault diagnostic system with the use of the Minutiae algorithm.

$$\text{erosion}(I, B)(x, y) = \min \{ I(x+i, y+j) : b(i, j) = 1 \}$$

where (x, y) represents a pixel position in the output eroded image, and (x+i, y+j) represents the corresponding pixel positions in the input image I based on the structuring element B.

The final output image is acquired as:

output_image = dilation (input_image, kernel) followed by erosion (output_image, kernel)

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to exhibit the superiority of the proposed diagnosis system, an experiment is conducted on a testing dataset to evaluate its performance. An enhanced testing image from the testing dataset is shown in Table II.

As mentioned above, a total of 60 testing signals were obtained. Table III shows the classification accuracy of all the testing signals. The experiment results indicate that each fault category can get high classification accuracy and the proposed system is effective in fault diagnosis of rotating machinery.

Accuracy measures the proportion of correctly classified instances out of the total number of instances in the dataset. Our model achieved an accuracy of 100% for the combined fault

type. For the loosened fault type, the achieved accuracy is 98.33% and for the unbalanced fault type, the achieved accuracy is 95%, indicating the ability of the proposed method to make correct predictions.

Minutiae algorithms are capable of capturing subtle changes in the data that may indicate the early stages of a fault or degradation in a machine. Early detection is essential for proactive maintenance, preventing catastrophic failures, reducing downtime, and minimizing repair costs. Minutiae algorithms can achieve high precision in fault diagnosis, thus reducing false alarms and ensuring that the identified faults are accurate and reliable.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the proposed Minutiae algorithm provides effective fault classification in rotating machinery diagnosis based on image recognition. The suggested image-recognition-based fault diagnostic technique for rotating machines first provides an image interest point extraction method to achieve feature extraction of RP automatically and to offer fault diagnosis. The results showed that this method can improve robustness and generalization ability while maintaining classification accuracy.

TABLE II. FREQUENCY SPECTRA IN THE TRAINING DATASET AND THEIR ENHANCED IMAGES

Fault type	Original	Processed image	Input image	Output images
Combined				
Loosened				
Unbalanced				

TABLE III. DIAGNOSIS RESULTS

Fault types	Testing samples	Correct results	Accuracy
Combined	60	60	100%
Looseness	60	59	98.33%
Unbalanced	60	57	95%

Minutiae algorithm is helpful in accurate early fault detection so that corrective action can take place to avoid failure of machines. Minutiae algorithms are essential components of modern machine fault diagnosis systems, providing the necessary tools to monitor, analyze, and predict faults in machinery, leading to improved reliability, safety, and

productivity in industrial settings. The performance of the suggested proposed on benchmark data sets is quite promising.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Zhang, B. Tang, and X. Xiao, "Time–frequency interpretation of multi-frequency signal from rotating machinery using an improved Hilbert–Huang transform," *Measurement*, vol. 82, pp. 221–239, Mar. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measurement.2016.01.001>.
- [2] H. Pan, Y. Yang, X. Li, J. Zheng, and J. Cheng, "Symplectic geometry mode decomposition and its application to rotating machinery compound fault diagnosis," *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*, vol. 114, pp. 189–211, Jan. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymssp.2018.05.019>.
- [3] M. Zhang, Z. Jiang, and K. Feng, "Research on variational mode decomposition in rolling bearings fault diagnosis of the multistage

- centrifugal pump," *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*, vol. 93, pp. 460–493, Sep. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymssp.2017.02.013>.
- [4] H. K. Srinivas, K. S. Srinivasan, and K. N. Umesh, "Application of Artificial Neural Network and Wavelet Transform for Vibration Analysis of Combined Faults of Unbalances and Shaft Bow," *Advances in Theoretical and Applied Mechanics*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 159–176, 2010.
- [5] Z. Zhang, Y. Wang, and K. Wang, "Fault diagnosis and prognosis using wavelet packet decomposition, Fourier transform and artificial neural network," *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing*, vol. 24, no. 6, pp. 1213–1227, Dec. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10845-012-0657-2>.
- [6] W. Deng, S. Zhang, H. Zhao, and X. Yang, "A Novel Fault Diagnosis Method Based on Integrating Empirical Wavelet Transform and Fuzzy Entropy for Motor Bearing," *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 35042–35056, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2834540>.
- [7] N. S. Vyas and D. Satishkumar, "Artificial neural network design for fault identification in a rotor-bearing system," *Mechanism and Machine Theory*, vol. 36, no. 2, pp. 157–175, Feb. 2001, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0094-114X\(00\)00034-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0094-114X(00)00034-3).
- [8] H. Ma, X. Zhao, Y. Teng, and B. Wen, "Analysis of Dynamic Characteristics for a Rotor System with Pedestal Looseness," *Shock and Vibration*, vol. 18, no. 1–2, pp. 13–27, 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2011/753047>.
- [9] M. C. S. Reddy and A. S. Sekhar, "Application of Artificial Neural Networks for Identification of Unbalance and Looseness in Rotor Bearing Systems," *International Journal of Applied Science and Engineering*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 69–84, 2013, [https://doi.org/10.6703/IJASE.2013.11\(1\).69](https://doi.org/10.6703/IJASE.2013.11(1).69).
- [10] G. Chen, Y. Liu, W. Zhou, and J. Song, "Research on intelligent fault diagnosis based on time series analysis algorithm," *The Journal of China Universities of Posts and Telecommunications*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 68–74, Mar. 2008, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1005-8885\(08\)60064-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1005-8885(08)60064-3).
- [11] C.-C. Wang, Y. Kang, P.-C. Shen, Y.-P. Chang, and Y.-L. Chung, "Applications of fault diagnosis in rotating machinery by using time series analysis with neural network," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 37, no. 2, pp. 1696–1702, Mar. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2009.06.089>.
- [12] A. Yaşar, A. Keskin, Ş. Yıldızhan, and E. Uludamar, "Emission and vibration analysis of diesel engine fuelled diesel fuel containing metallic based nanoparticles," *Fuel*, vol. 239, pp. 1224–1230, Mar. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2018.11.113>.
- [13] H. Liu and M. Han, "A fault diagnosis method based on local mean decomposition and multi-scale entropy for roller bearings," *Mechanism and Machine Theory*, vol. 75, pp. 67–78, May 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mechmachtheory.2014.01.011>.
- [14] Q. Hu, X.-S. Si, Q.-H. Zhang, and A.-S. Qin, "A rotating machinery fault diagnosis method based on multi-scale dimensionless indicators and random forests," *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*, vol. 139, May 2020, Art. no. 106609, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymssp.2019.106609>.
- [15] R. Yan, R. X. Gao, and X. Chen, "Wavelets for fault diagnosis of rotary machines: A review with applications," *Signal Processing*, vol. 96, pp. 1–15, Mar. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sigpro.2013.04.015>.
- [16] H. Ahmed and A. K. Nandi, *Condition Monitoring with Vibration Signals: Compressive Sampling and Learning Algorithms for Rotating Machines*, 1st ed. Hoboken, NJ, USA: Wiley-IEEE Press, 2020.
- [17] V. K. Rai and A. R. Mohanty, "Bearing fault diagnosis using FFT of intrinsic mode functions in Hilbert–Huang transform," *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*, vol. 21, no. 6, pp. 2607–2615, Aug. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymssp.2006.12.004>.
- [18] S. Fei and X. Zhang, "Fault diagnosis of power transformer based on support vector machine with genetic algorithm," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 36, no. 8, pp. 11352–11357, Oct. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2009.03.022>.
- [19] S. Khan, I. Ali, F. Ghaffar, and Q. Mazhar-ul-Haq, "Classification of Macromolecules Based on Amino Acid Sequences Using Deep Learning," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 9491–9495, Dec. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5230>.
- [20] M. Sreenatha and P. B. Mallikarjuna, "A Fault Diagnosis Technique for Wind Turbine Gearbox: An Approach using Optimized BLSTM Neural Network with Undercomplete Autoencoder," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 10170–10174, Feb. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5595>.
- [21] M. O. Genc and N. Kaya, "Vibration Damping Optimization using Simulated Annealing Algorithm for Vehicle Powertrain System," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 5164–5167, Feb. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3242>.

Design and Optical Performance of a Single-Junction GaAs Nanowire-Ge Solar Cell

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ABSTRACT

Solar cells are one of the most effective methods available for energy harvesting and are constructed from a variety of materials. In recent years, the use of novel materials for low-cost, high-efficiency photovoltaics has been one of the most exciting breakthroughs. This study conducted an in-depth investigation into the optical characteristics of GaAs nanowires on a Ge bottom cell. Geometric optimization of nanowires is necessary to increase solar cell performance metrics. The absorption efficiency per unit volume was considerably boosted over its traditional bulk and thin-film counterparts as a result of inherent antireflection, intensive stimulation of resonant modes, and optical antenna effects. A 3D FDTD framework was used to acquire optical properties and incorporate numerical values. Under typical AM 1.5G illumination, the diameter of GaAs nanowires was optimized to 170 nm.

Keywords-absorption; E&H field; FDTD; GaAs nanowire; III-V semiconductor nanowires; optical simulation

I. INTRODUCTION

The utilization of solar energy is significant for meeting future energy demands at low cost. In the photovoltaic (PV) market, thin-film technology is gaining great attention due to its simplicity, ease of fabrication, reduced dimensions [1], light weight [2], and reduced cost, among the various types of solar cells. However, the thin-film technology has major disadvantages, such as a reduction in solar conversion efficiency in longer spectral regions due to reduced absorption [1]. To overcome this problem, researchers adopt various strategies to improve efficiency while preserving its advantages. To do so, the amount of light trapping mechanisms is increased by using several dielectric and metallic nanostructures in various dimensions, such as diffractive gratings, textured electrodes, photonic crystals, antireflection coatings, nanoparticles, nanowires (NW), nanofillers, etc. [3].

Of all these different nanostructures, NW-based solar cells are quite popular for improving optical performance in PV devices, as they show improved electrical and optical properties compared to traditional wafer- or thin-film-based

solar cells [4]. The ability to capture an enormous amount of light, decrease reflection, fine-tune the band gap, and improve defect tolerance are just a few advantages [4-5]. To realize these NW structures, thin film solar cells are integrated using different materials, such as silicon, II-VI group, III-V group, etc. [6]. Furthermore, because of their direct bandgap structure, high absorption coefficient [7], and strong resistance to high energy rays in space, III-V group semiconducting materials are attracting a lot of attention, particularly for solar space applications [8]. However, gallium-arsenide (GaAs)-based thin-film solar cells showed the highest efficiency, up to 29.1% higher than others, such as III-V materials [9]. Due to the limitations in the efficiency of single-junction solar cells, tandem cells are developed [9].

GaAs nanostructures over germanium (Ge) substrates are one such configuration of two-junction solar cells. Ge provides considerable advantages, such as a perfect match of lattice constant and thermal expansion [11], remarkable strength, and low weight [10], leading to improvements in optical properties and cell efficiency. GaAs solar cells have great radiation resistance and low temperature coefficients to achieve high

conversion efficiency [10]. Since GaAs has a higher optical absorption band, it is well suited for solar energy conversion. Combining GaAs with a Ge bottom cell, which shares the same lattice constant, allows the creation of solar cells [9].

This study focused on the optical modeling of a GaAs single NWs on a Ge cell bottom and a vertical junction. The optimized length and diameter of GaAs NW (L and D) were used to calculate the absorption, transmittance, and reflection characteristics curves for fixed length and pitch in a 0.5 ratio for the highest absorption and cell efficiency. In solar cell design, the D/P ratio is called the Fill Factor, where D is the diameter of the nanowire and P is the highest power output of the solar cell (Pmax). Pmax is the highest amount of electricity that a solar cell can produce under certain conditions. The Pmax value is not a fixed constant, as it can change depending on irradiance (the intensity of light hitting the solar cell), temperature, and the external load connected to the solar cell during testing. Because of this, the Pmax value is specific to how the solar cell works. Different materials have different absorption characteristics and can absorb light more efficiently at certain wavelengths. In general, if a material has an increased absorptance at shorter wavelengths, it means that it is more effective at absorbing light in that range. At shorter wavelengths, the behavior of light can be influenced by factors such as the energy band structure of the material and the electronic transitions that occur. In certain materials or structures, such as thin films or coatings, it is possible to design them to minimize reflection and transmission losses at shorter wavelengths. It is important to note that the specific behavior of materials for absorbance, reflection, and transmission at different wavelengths can vary significantly depending on the material's composition, structure, and other factors. Different materials may exhibit different optical properties, making them more suitable for specific applications.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Solar cells are widely used in optoelectronic devices based on their geometry to analyze the effects of size, height, band gap, and PV efficiency with III-V semiconductor nanomaterials such as GaAs NWs [14-15]. Current production conditions have shown that GaAs/inactive-Ge cells can provide a larger area, reduced weight, and high-efficiency cells due to their monolithic tandem [6, 16]. Single NWs are used in the design of solar cells to provide better performance with different geometries [6-7] while introducing a Ge (111) substrate interdiffused with GaAs in a selected area [17].

The absorption of light from a one-dimensional semiconductor nanostructure can be used to guide the development of highly efficient NW solar cells [18]. Various complications arise when designing solar cells in three dimensions, such as studying the thickness and structural interaction between layers [10]. The structure of SOI solar cells is used to justify the optical performance of antennas [19]. The absorption efficiency is greatly improved when an NW is incorporated into the design of a solar cell [20]. Maximum power (Pmax), voltage (Voc), and light scattering coefficient (Lsc) can change when designing omnidirectional solar cells with a silicon material, although GaAs/Ge solar cells have been modeled in both proton and electron environments [21].

Unlike NWs, the use of nanofluids explains the passage of energy from one port to another, specifies absorption and scattering parameters, and improves the interaction between nanoparticles [22]. These solar cells are used to achieve high efficiency [23] due to the electric field interaction that occurs between them and the electric charge when it passes through space or an electrical conductor. In [24], the electric field and electrical parameters of a stacked model design of GaAs/Ge solar cells were examined in MATLAB under ordinary settings. In [25], numerical FDTD software was used to investigate the optical and electrical properties of different NW diameters, achieving a maximum absorptance of 94% in a wavelength range of 320-455 nm, while increasing the wavelength range the absorptance efficiency decreased. In [26], III-V and II-VI semiconducting materials were integrated to investigate the optoelectronic device physics simulations of GaAs NW solar cells, including recombination models such as heterojunction solar cells, and the optimal design for high efficiency was discussed. In [27], optoelectronic simulations of GaAs NW solar cells showed that efficiency can be improved by optimizing the emitter thickness and extending the intrinsic region. In [28], III-V semiconductor nanomaterials were found to have high electron mobility, a tunable optical bandgap, and suitable optical and electrical properties for photodetection over a broad spectrum range, from deep ultraviolet to THz. In [29], it was shown that the electric field of a GaAs solar cell decreases with increasing incident light intensity due to the PV effect. In [30], the optical properties of III-V semiconductor nanomaterials and their potential for all-optical switching applications were analyzed. In [31], a method for manufacturing tandem solar cells was described using crystalline silicon substrates.

III. SIMULATION METHODOLOGY

Simulations of optical components were carried out using CST's commercial 3D FDTD software. GaAs nanowires were prepared with a diameter (D) ranging from 50 to 200 nm, while their lengths (L) and the length of the Ge bottom cell (P) were maintained at 340 and 50 nm, respectively, and the D/P ratio was maintained constant at 0.5 to determine the best solution. An AM 1.5G light source spanning between 300-2000 nm was used to illuminate the system under study. Periodic boundary conditions were imposed along the z-axis using precisely matched layer methods in the x and y directions.

The absorption coefficient $A(\lambda)$ is the proportion of the incident light at a given wavelength that is retained by the medium it encounters. $T(\lambda)$ is the percentage of a given wavelength of light that passes completely through a certain substance or medium without being absorbed or reflected. $R(\lambda)$ is the percentage of a beam's energy that is reflected from a substance or medium at a certain wavelength. Light at every given wavelength λ is absorbed at a $A(\lambda)$ rate, transmitted at a $T(\lambda)$ rate, and reflected at a $R(\lambda)$ rate. The values of reflectance $R(\lambda)$ and transmission $T(\lambda)$ are determined with the help of frequency domain power monitors. For each given wavelength, $E(\lambda)$ represents the energy of the incident light. The absorbed energy (A) is given by $A(\lambda) \times E(\lambda)$, the transmitted energy (T) is given by $T(\lambda) \times E(\lambda)$, and the reflected energy (R) is given by $R(\lambda) \times E(\lambda)$. As the energy of incident light is conserved,

the sum of the energy absorbed, transmitted, and reflected must equal the energy of the incident light:

$$T(\lambda) \times E(\lambda) + A(\lambda) \times E(\lambda) + R(\lambda) \times E(\lambda) = E(\lambda) \quad (1)$$

$$T(\lambda) + A(\lambda) + R(\lambda) = 1 \quad (2)$$

For a system in which light interacts with a material or medium, the law of energy conservation is represented by (2). These parameters were used to simulate the optical properties of a single GaAs NW on a Ge bottom cell with a 0.5 D/P ratio.

IV. DESIGNING

Figure 1 shows the simulated optical wavefront for an irradiated by sunlight single GaAs NW placed atop a Ge bottom cell.

Fig. 1. Top: solar cell top, vertical junction view. Bottom: mesh view.

A boundary condition for the simulating medium was implemented to account for additional loose media on all sides of the simulation zone when modeling a GaAs NW solar cell. As a result, there is no reflection at the interfaces and the inherent impedance matches. GaAs NW and Ge subcell surfaces attenuate electromagnetic fields during propagation inside the media. Measurements of absorption, reflectance, and transmission were taken once the nanowire diameter was optimized for maximum performance.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 2 shows the transmission, reflection, and absorption spectra of a 170 nm-diameter axial GaAs NW. As the wavelength increases, the strong extinction coefficient of GaAs and the wide bandgap difference between the GaAs NW and the Ge bottom cell cause the peak absorbance (near unity) to

fall ($\lambda > 800$ nm). A rise in refraction losses is responsible for the drop in absorption spectra between 1000 and 1500 nm. A material having a bandgap between GaAs and Ge can be used to reduce this loss. At an increase in transparency of over 1000 nm, the NW and bottom-cell systems disappear from view. Impedance spectroscopy is used to study the kinetics and energetic processes that govern device performance in both inorganic and organic solar cells. It is also a valuable tool for examining bulk and interfacial electrical properties that cannot be studied under present experimental circumstances. In this technique, a bias voltage is used in conjunction with a tiny sinusoidal voltage. By fitting data from a measurement of an electrical impedance to a circuit model, insight can be gained into the resistance and capacitance of individual cells.

Fig. 2. (a) Absorbance, (b) reflectance, and (c) transmittance of the GaAs NW vertical junction solar cell.

Now, the discussion is on the different field types present in solar cells. One type of field is an electric field (E-field). Solar cells are capable of converting sunlight into electricity. The E-field within a solar cell is an important factor in its operation. As photons strike a solar cell, they excite electrons and cause

them to travel from the valence band to the conduction band, producing an electrical current. The electric field within the solar cell helps to separate the excited electrons from their positively charged counterparts called holes and move them in the right direction to generate electricity. A p-n junction generates the E-field in a solar cell. The solar cell consists of two distinct materials with varying electrical characteristics in this region. The junction creates an E-field that points from the p-type material to the n-type material, and this field helps to separate the excited electrons and holes. In general, the electric field in a solar cell plays a crucial role in its ability to generate electricity from sunlight. Figures 4, 5, and 6 represent the E-field for different port wavelengths of 0.5, 1.35, and 2nm, respectively, and the field passes from Port 1 to Port 2 of the GaAs NW solar cell.

Fig. 3. Impedance of the vertical junction GaAs NW solar cell.

Fig. 4. E-field of the GaAs NW solar cell with a wavelength of 0.5nm from Port 1 to Port 2.

Fig. 5. E-field of the GaAs NW solar cell with a wavelength of 1.35nm from Port 1 to Port 2.

Fig. 6. E-field of the GaAs NW solar cell with a wavelength of 2nm from Port 1 to Port 2.

The magnetic field (H-field) is not directly involved in the operation of solar cells. Instead, solar cells rely on the E-field to generate electricity. The movement of charged particles, such as electrons and holes, within the semiconductor material of the solar cell is what generates the E-field. However, magnetic fields can have an impact on solar cells. Magnetic fields can induce an electric current in a conductor such as the wiring and metal components of a solar cell. This current, called an eddy current, can cause loss and heat within the solar cell, reducing its efficiency. As a result, while constructing and installing solar cells, it is critical to consider the magnetic field environment, particularly in areas with large magnetic fields, such as near power lines or electrical equipment. Figures 7, 8, and 9 represent the H-field for port wavelengths 0.5, 1.35, and 2 nm, respectively, and the field passes from Port 1 to Port 2 of the GaAs NW solar cell. At port wavelength 1.35 nm, the E-field and the H-field operate effectively on the assumed dimensions.

Fig. 7. H-Field of the GaAs NW solar cell with a wavelength of 0.5nm from Port 1 to Port 2.

Fig. 8. H-Field of the GaAs NW solar cell with a wavelength of 1.35nm from Port 1 to Port 2.

Fig. 9. H-Field of the GaAs NW solar cell with a wavelength of 2nm from Port 1 to Port 2.

Table I shows the percentage of absorptance and reflectance with different radii of NW within the range of $\lambda = 1000-1800$ nm. Figures 10 and 11 show the absorption and reflection for different radii of GaAs NW. It can be noted that there is increased absorbtance and reduced reflection at shorter wavelengths of 1000-1800 nm.

TABLE I. ABSORPTANCE AND REFLECTANCE FOR DIFFERENT NANOWIRE RADIUS

Radius (nm)	$\lambda = 1000-1800$ nm	
	Maximum Absorptance (%)	Minimum Reflectance (%)
85	99	0.9
90	94	5.8
95	91	8.7
100	87	11.5

Fig. 10. Absorption spectra for different GaAs NW radii.

Fig. 11. Reflectance results for different GaAs NW radii.

Depending on the radius of the NW and how much light is reflected or transmitted, a certain mode will resonate, governing its light absorption. Understanding the relationships between NWs' geometrical characteristics and their various light-absorbing mechanisms is crucial for achieving maximum light absorption. In this process, a maximum absorptance of 99% was obtained at a 1243-1397 nm wavelength with an NW radius of 85 nm.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study used the 3D FDTD approach implemented in CST software to conduct a comprehensive analysis of GaAs NW with Ge bottom-cell solar cells to optimize their geometrical characteristics and study their solar cell performance in E-Field and H-Field at varying port wavelengths. The electrical properties of a GaAs NW cylinder had a maximum absorptance of 99% in the wavelength range

of 1243-1397 nm for a radius of 85 nm. Its absorptance was 94%, 91%, and 87% when the radius was 90, 95, and 100 nm. Therefore, as the radius of the GaAs nanowire cylinder increases, the absorptance percentage decreases. The electric field and magnetic field of a single junction GaAs - Ge solar cell were determined with different port wavelengths of 0.5, 1.35, and 2 nm. It was observed that at 1.35nm, the E-field and H-field were conducted and provided better optical and electrical properties.

REFERENCES

- [1] I. Mora-Seró, G. Garcia-Belmonte, P. P. Boix, M. A. Vázquez, and J. Bisquert, "Impedance spectroscopy characterisation of highly efficient silicon solar cells under different light illumination intensities," *Energy & Environmental Science*, vol. 2, no. 6, pp. 678–686, 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1039/B812468J>.
- [2] R. Anil Kumar, M. S. Suresh, and J. Nagaraju, "Measurement and comparison of AC parameters of silicon (BSR and BSFR) and gallium arsenide (GaAs/Ge) solar cells used in space applications," *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, vol. 60, no. 2, pp. 155–166, Jan. 2000, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0927-0248\(99\)00080-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0927-0248(99)00080-X).
- [3] G. Garcia-Belmonte, P. P. Boix, J. Bisquert, M. Sessolo, and H. J. Bolink, "Simultaneous determination of carrier lifetime and electron density-of-states in P3HT:PCBM organic solar cells under illumination by impedance spectroscopy," *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, vol. 94, no. 2, pp. 366–375, Feb. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2009.10.015>.
- [4] T. Ripolles-Sanchis, A. Guerrero, J. Bisquert, and G. Garcia-Belmonte, "Diffusion-Recombination Determines Collected Current and Voltage in Polymer:Fullerene Solar Cells," *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C*, vol. 116, no. 32, pp. 16925–16933, Aug. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp305941f>.
- [5] D. V. Prashant, D. P. Samajdar, and D. Sharma, "Optical simulation and geometrical optimization of P3HT/GaAs nanowire hybrid solar cells for maximal photocurrent generation via enhanced light absorption," *Solar Energy*, vol. 194, pp. 848–855, Dec. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2019.11.027>.
- [6] S. P. Tobin, S. M. Vernon, C. Bajgar, V. E. Haven, L. M. Geoffroy, and D. R. Lillington, "High-efficiency GaAs/Ge monolithic tandem solar cells," *IEEE Electron Device Letters*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 256–258, Feb. 1988, <https://doi.org/10.1109/55.708>.
- [7] Z. Li, H. H. Tan, C. Jagadish, and L. Fu, "III-V Semiconductor Single Nanowire Solar Cells: A Review," *Advanced Materials Technologies*, vol. 3, no. 9, 2018, Art. no. 1800005, <https://doi.org/10.1002/admt.201800005>.
- [8] E. C. Garnett, M. L. Brongersma, Y. Cui, and M. D. McGehee, "Nanowire Solar Cells," *Annual Review of Materials Research*, vol. 41, no. 1, pp. 269–295, 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-matsci-062910-100434>.
- [9] Sachchidanand and D. P. Samajdar, "Light-trapping strategy for PEDOT:PSS/c-Si nanopillar based hybrid solar cells embedded with metallic nanoparticles," *Solar Energy*, vol. 190, pp. 278–285, Sep. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2019.08.023>.
- [10] J.-P. Berenger, "A perfectly matched layer for the absorption of electromagnetic waves," *Journal of Computational Physics*, vol. 114, no. 2, pp. 185–200, Oct. 1994, <https://doi.org/10.1006/jcph.1994.1159>.
- [11] L. Cao *et al.*, "Semiconductor Nanowire Optical Antenna Solar Absorbers," *Nano Letters*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 439–445, Feb. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1021/nl9036627>.
- [12] J. Z. Zhang, *Optical Properties And Spectroscopy Of Nanomaterials*. Singapore: World Scientific, 2009.
- [13] J. Wong-Leung *et al.*, "Engineering III-V Semiconductor Nanowires for Device Applications," *Advanced Materials*, vol. 32, no. 18, 2020, Art. no. 1904359, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201904359>.
- [14] Z. Gu, P. Prete, N. Lovergine, and B. Nabet, "On optical properties of GaAs and GaAs/AlGaAs core-shell periodic nanowire arrays," *Journal*

- of *Applied Physics*, vol. 109, no. 6, Mar. 2011, Art. no. 064314, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3555096>.
- [15] L. Wen, Z. Zhao, X. Li, Y. Shen, H. Guo, and Y. Wang, "Theoretical analysis and modeling of light trapping in high efficiency GaAs nanowire array solar cells," *Applied Physics Letters*, vol. 99, no. 14, Oct. 2011, Art. no. 143116, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3647847>.
- [16] P. A. Iles, Y. C. M. Yeh, F. H. Ho, C. L. Chu, and C. Cheng, "High-efficiency (>20% AM0) GaAs solar cells grown on inactive-Ge substrates," *IEEE Electron Device Letters*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 140–142, Apr. 1990, <https://doi.org/10.1109/55.61775>.
- [17] Y. Minami, A. Yoshida, J. Motohisa, and K. Tomioka, "Growth and characterization of GaAs nanowires on Ge(1 1 1) substrates by selective-area MOVPE," *Journal of Crystal Growth*, vol. 506, pp. 135–139, Jan. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcrysgro.2018.10.009>.
- [18] T. J. Kempa, R. W. Day, S.-K. Kim, H.-G. Park, and C. M. Lieber, "Semiconductor nanowires: a platform for exploring limits and concepts for nano-enabled solar cells," *Energy & Environmental Science*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 719–733, Feb. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C3EE24182C>.
- [19] E. S. Barnard, R. A. Pala, and M. L. Brongersma, "Photocurrent mapping of near-field optical antenna resonances," *Nature Nanotechnology*, vol. 6, no. 9, pp. 588–593, Sep. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nnano.2011.131>.
- [20] J. Kupec, R. L. Stoop, and B. Witzigmann, "Light absorption and emission in nanowire array solar cells," *Optics Express*, vol. 18, no. 26, pp. 27589–27605, Dec. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1364/OE.18.027589>.
- [21] J. Kupec, R. L. Stoop, and B. Witzigmann, "Light absorption and emission in nanowire array solar cells," *Optics Express*, vol. 18, no. 26, pp. 27589–27605, Dec. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1364/OE.18.027589>.
- [22] H. A. Fakhim, "An Investigation of the Effect of Different Nanofluids in a Solar Collector," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 1741–1745, Aug. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1283>.
- [23] M. E. Bendib and A. Mekias, "Solar Panel and Wireless Power Transmission System as a Smart Grid for Electric Vehicles," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 5683–5688, Jun. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3473>.
- [24] S. E. T. Moghaddam and S. M. Kankanani, "Numerical Simulation of a Mechanically Stacked GaAs/Ge Solar Cell," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 1611–1614, Jun. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.935>.
- [25] L. M. Ali and F. A. Abed, "Investigation of opto-electric characterization of GaAs/In_{0.2}Ga_{0.8}As nanowire solar cell," *Materials Research Express*, vol. 6, no. 4, Jan. 2019, Art. no. 045062, <https://doi.org/10.1088/2053-1591/aaffee>.
- [26] P. R. Jahelka and H. A. Atwater, "Non-Epitaxial GaAs Heterojunction Nanowire Solar Cells (PVSC)," in *2019 IEEE 46th Photovoltaic Specialists Conference (PVSC)*, Chicago, IL, USA, Jun. 2019, vol. 2, pp. 1–8, <https://doi.org/10.1109/PVSC40753.2019.9198966>.
- [27] A. H. Trojnar, C. E. Valdivia, R. R. LaPierre, K. Hinzer, and J. J. Krich, "Optimizations of GaAs Nanowire Solar Cells," *IEEE Journal of Photovoltaics*, vol. 6, no. 6, pp. 1494–1501, Aug. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1109/JPHOTOV.2016.2600339>.
- [28] K. Sarkar, P. Devi, K.-H. Kim, and P. Kumar, "III-V nanowire-based ultraviolet to terahertz photodetectors: Device strategies, recent developments, and future possibilities," *TrAC Trends in Analytical Chemistry*, vol. 130, Sep. 2020, Art. no. 115989, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2020.115989>.
- [29] S. SaeidNahaie *et al.*, "Investigation of the incident light intensity effect on the internal electric fields of GaAs single junction solar cell using bright electroreflectance spectroscopy," *Current Applied Physics*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 145–149, Jan. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cap.2019.10.006>.
- [30] V. Snigirev, A. Shorokhov, D. Gulkin, V. Bessonov, I. Soboleva, and A. Fedyanin, "Ultrafast all-optical switching in III-V semiconductor resonant nanostructures," in *2019 Conference on Lasers and Electro-Optics Europe and European Quantum Electronics Conference (2019)*, Munich, Germany, Jun. 2019.
- [31] Y. J. Lee, S. KIM, S.-W. Ahn, and J.-W. Chung, "Tandem solar cell manufacturing method," US11515443B2, Nov. 29, 2022.

Manta Ray Foraging Optimizer with Deep Learning-based Fundus Image Retrieval and Classification for Diabetic Retinopathy Grading

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ABSTRACT

Diabetic Retinopathy (DR) is a major source of sightlessness and permanent visual damage. Manual Analysis of DR is a labor-intensive and costly task that requires skilled ophthalmologists to observe and evaluate DR utilizing digital fundus images. The images can be employed for analysis and disease screening. This laborious task can gain a great advantage in automated detection by exploiting Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques. Content-Based Image Retrieval (CBIR) approaches are utilized to retrieve related images in massive databases and are helpful in many application regions and most healthcare systems. With this motivation, this article develops the new Manta Ray Foraging Optimizer with Deep Learning-based Fundus Image Retrieval and Classification (MRFODL-FIRC) approach for the grading of DR. The suggested MRFODL-FIRC model investigates the retinal fundus imaging effectively to retrieve the relevant images and identify class labels. To achieve this, the MRFODL-FIRC technique uses Median Filtering (MF) as a pre-processing step. The Capsule Network (CapsNet) model is used to produce feature vectors with the MRFO algorithm as a hyperparameter optimizer. For the image retrieval process, the Manhattan distance metric is used. Finally, the Variational Autoencoder (VAE) model is used for recognizing and classifying DR. The investigational assessment of the MRFODL-FIRC technique is accomplished on medical DR and the outputs highlighted the improved performance of the MRFODL-FIRC algorithm over the current approaches.

Keywords-fundus images; image classification; diabetic retinopathy; deep learning; Manta Ray foraging optimization

I. INTRODUCTION

Diabetic Retinopathy (DR) denotes a complication of diabetes that happens due to damaged Blood Vessels (BVs) in the retina caused by higher blood sugar levels, leading to leaking and swelling in BV [1]. The vision can be completely lost in an advanced DR phase. Currently, ophthalmologists routinely use digital retinal fundus images for grading and classifying DR [2]. During this process, the ophthalmologist must visually observe digital fundus images, compare those with standard images such as EDTRS images, or images from archival DR image datasets, for interpreting images with more accuracy or for clarifying confusion [3]. This procedure is vulnerable to error or review fatigue and is a laborious process. The ophthalmologists find it difficult to use a large volume of past medical reports with proven pathology because they are not readily accessible to the historical medical reports that are appropriate to a new image that has to be identified [4]. Thus,

the enormous quantity of diagnosis knowledge concealed in historical databases has been wasted [5].

Images can be medically relevant if they comprise similar kinds of lesions having the same visual appearance [6]. One method that has proved very beneficial in the early diagnosis of retinal diseases is the CBIR method. The fundus images obtained from many diabetic patients are useful data for analysing retinal diseases with the help of image processing methods. The CBIR process has two stages in it [7], the feature extraction stage and the query matching stage. In the first stage, a feature vector is generated by extracting features like texture, color, and shape of images. Feature vector is an optimized form of imagery [8]. Query matching depends on similarity measurement, which makes use of the distance of the query from all images in the database to detect the closest image. It is a time-consuming process if done manually, it needs significant effort, and may lead to misdiagnosis [9]. Hence, to reduce the overall cost and avoid misdiagnosis, time, and effort,

Computer-Aided Detection (CAD) methods can be used as potential means. In the past, Deep Learning (DL) techniques have been applied in several domains, including medical image analysis [10]. DL has the potential to detect features precisely from input datasets for segmentation or classification and normally outpaces all classical image analysis methods.

In the current study, the new Manta Ray Foraging Optimizer with Deep Learning based Fundus Image Retrieval and Classification (MRFODL-FIRC) approach for the grading of DR. The presented MRFODL-FIRC approach exploits Median Filtering (MF) as a pre-processing step. The Capsule Network (CapsNet) model is used to produce feature vectors with the MRFO algorithm as a hyperparameter optimizer. For the image retrieval process, the Manhattan distance metric is used. Finally, the Variational Autoencoder (VAE) model is used for recognizing and classifying DR. The investigational assessment of the MRFODL-FIRC technique is accomplished on a medical DR dataset.

II. RELATED WORKS

Authors in [11] introduced the new diabetic retinopathy screening algorithm utilizing an asymmetric DL feature. Through U-Net for BV segmentation and optic disc, the asymmetric DL features were derived. For the DR lesion classification, a CNN with an SVM was utilized. The lesions were categorized into 4 classes, i.e. haemorrhages, normal, exudates, and microaneurysms. Author in [12], presented a two-step training approach using a supervised contrastive loss function called SCL technique for identifying the DR and its robust phases from fundus image. The pre-trained Xception CNN method was deployed as the encoder with TL and the CLAHE model was implemented to enrich the image quality. The SNE technique was utilized to visualize embedding space made up of 128D space into 2D space to interpret the SCL model. Authors in [13] suggested a dual-phase technique for the automatically classification of DR. Due to the lower fraction of positive samples in the BV and asymmetric Optic Disk (OD) detection system, data augmentation and pre-processing methods were utilized for enriching the image quantity and quality. The first step utilized 2 U-Net approaches for OD and BV segmentation. After pre-processing, the symmetric fusion CNN-SVD algorithm was employed to choose and extract the discriminative factors followed by BV and OD extraction through InceptionV3 depending on TL. Authors in [14] introduced ML-CAD systems that visualized the pathological variations and identified DR images. Firstly, the authors reduced noise, standardized the size, and enhanced the quality of the retinal images. Then, by computing the gray-level average of run length matrix in 4 diverse directions, the authors distinguished between the DR and healthy cases with the help of a DL method (UNet). The system mechanically derived 4 major classes: haemorrhages, BVs, microaneurysms, and exudates.

Authors in [15] presented a DL-related technique for automatically evaluating DR in retina FIs. For increasing the discriminative capability of the retrieved features, a multi-scale attention system was implemented in a deep CNN structure. A brand-new loss function termed modified grading loss was provided that boosts the training convergence of the suggested

method by considering the distance between different grades of various DR categories. Authors in [16] devised an innovative technique for precise haemorrhage detection from retinal images. Initially, this technique makes use of the contrast advancement approach to enrich the edge information from input fundus imaging. Next, an innovative CNN structure was devised for identifying haemorrhages. An adapted pretrained CNN technique was utilized for extracting features from identified haemorrhages. In stage 3, each extracted feature vector was merged through the convolutional sparse image decomposition algorithm.

III. THE PROPOSED MODEL

In this research, an automatic DR grading and classification model, named the MRFODL-FIRC technique is developed. The proposed MRFODL-FIRC technique examines retinal fundus images efficaciously for retrieving related images and determining the classes. It encompasses different sub-processes, namely MF-based pre-processing, CapsNet-based feature extracting process, MRFO-based tuning process, Manhattan distance-based similarity measurement, and VAE classification. Figure 1 demonstrates the comprehensive flow of the MRFODL-FIRC model.

Fig. 1. Overall flow of the MRFODL-FIRC approach.

A. MF-based Preprocessing

At first, the MF technique is used to pre-process the fundus images. MF is a procedure utilized to remove noise in the image [17]. This mechanism is exchanging all the pixels from the image with the median value of their neighboring pixels. The simple steps contained in MF are:

- Select the size of filter window: This window is classically a square or rectangular region centred in the pixel being filtered.
- Slide the filter window on the image: The filtering window is then slid on the image, one pixel at a time.
- Compute the median value: the median value of the pixel in the filter window can be computed for every pixel of the image.
- Exchange the pixel with the median value: The pixel being filtered is then exchanged by the computed median value.

B. Feature Extraction using the CapsNet Model

To produce feature vectors, the CapsNet model is utilized. CapsNet is a kind of NN which contains a set of neurons from which activity vectors point out the instantiate parameter of a specific entity [18], for instance, an object or object portion. It integrates 2 convolution layers with an entirely associated layer (termed as RecCaps). The 1st layer is utilized for converting the character images of the input as activation blocks. The second layer performs as PrimaryCaps. The modification of "neurons" with a singular scalar output was completed to PrimaryCaps with an 8-dimension vector procedure. Lastly, the the RecCaps layer is utilized for encapsulating the spatial connection amongst every local feature in the PrimaryCaps. Afterwards every feature can be provided as a superior dimension advanced capsule taking a dimension of 16. During the final layers, this method utilizes a nonlinear "squashing" activation function for ensuring the decrease of vector lengths from 0 to 1. This formula demonstrated provides the resultant vector of capsule j .

$$Y_m = \frac{\|X_m\|^2}{1 + \|X_m\|^2} \frac{X_m}{\|X_m\|} \quad (1)$$

where Y_m signifies the resultant vector for capsule m and X_m denotes the input vector.

Accordingly, the length of the capsule's resultant vector is utilized for representing the possibility of recovered local features. The lower-level factors in the input character can be removed by the first layer termed as *Conv1*. Afterwards, the primary capsule layer is utilized for applying convolution functions on the chosen group of features for acquiring 3D matrices. The dimensions of the matrices are $18 \times 16 \times 128$ and lastly, the matrices are gathered as 16 capsules. Each matrix has dimensions of $18 \times 16 \times 8$. An overall of 4680 capsules can be attained by utilizing squashing activation function once the stacking and flattening of capsules are completed. The extraction feature f_n is signified as 8-dimension vectors for each capsule.

The dynamic routing technique was utilized for recognizing a part of PrimaryCaps that is highly co-relatable with advanced capsules which determine the local features which are best probably connected to higher-level features. This procedure supports creating a model added to spatial connection needed for interpreting and detecting handwritten words. For every iteration, the coupling coefficient can be computed. Afterwards, the resultant vector for the capsule of the subsequent layer can be calculated. Lastly, the sum of

agreements among every capsule proceeds to the last outcome obtained.

C. Hyperparameter Tuning with the MRFO Algorithm

In this work, the MRFO algorithm adjusts the hyperparameters of the CapsNet model. Authors in [19] proposed MRFO as a nature-inspired metaheuristic that was applied to resolve different optimization issues [19]. The primary motivation of the MRFO derives from the behavior of Manta Rays (MRs) when capturing food. Somersault foraging, chain foraging, and cyclone foraging are the 3 major foraging approaches in the MRFO algorithm.

1) Chain Foraging

In this phase, MRs start foraging by moving sequentially and forming head-to-tail chains. Apart from the first individual, the others move towards the food and nearby MRs for cooperation. The chain foraging can be mathematically modelled as:

$$p_i^{t+1} = \begin{cases} p_i^t + r \cdot (p_{Best} - p_i^t) + \alpha \cdot (p_{Best} - p_i^t), & i = 1 \\ p_i^t + r \cdot (p_{i-1}^t - p_i^t) + \alpha \cdot (p_{Best} - p_i^t), & i = 2, \dots, N \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$$\alpha = 2 \cdot r \cdot \sqrt{\log(r)} \quad (3)$$

In (2), p_i^t signifies the i -th individual location at t iteration, r denotes a randomly generated integer within $[0,1]$, α denotes a weighted coefficient and p_{Best} signifies the optimum found location.

2) Cyclone Foraging

This approach is considered as the spiral displacement of MRs towards the prey as follows:

$$p_i^{t+1} = \begin{cases} p_i^t + r \cdot (p_{Best} - p_i^t) + \beta \cdot (p_{Best} - p_i^t), & i = 1 \\ p_i^t + r \cdot (p_{i-1}^t - p_i^t) + \beta \cdot (p_{Best} - p_i^t), & i = 2, \dots, N \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$p_{rand} = Lb + r \cdot (Ub - Lb) \quad (5)$$

$$p_i^{t+1} = \begin{cases} p_i^t + r \cdot (p_{rand} - p_i^t) + \beta \cdot (p_{rand} - p_i^t), & i = 1 \\ p_i^t + r \cdot (p_{i-1}^t - p_i^t) + \beta \cdot (p_{rand} - p_i^t), & i = 2, \dots, N \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

$$\beta = 2 \cdot e^{(r_1 \frac{T-t+1}{T})} \cdot \sin(2 \cdot \pi \cdot r_1) \quad (7)$$

where T shows the maximal number of iterations, p_{rand} characterizes a randomized location in the space defined by lower and higher boundaries Lb and Ub , β represents a weight coefficient, and r_1 denotes a random value within $[0,1]$.

3) Somersault Foraging

In such cases, the location of the prey is represented as a pivot. The MRs will be swimming toward the food and somersault to the newest location:

$$p_i^{t+1} = p_i^t + S \cdot (r_2 \cdot p_{Best} - r_3 \cdot p_i^t), \quad i = 1, \dots, N \quad (8)$$

where S characterizes the somersault feature set to 2, r_2 and r_3 are randomly generated numbers within $[0,1]$. The MRFO manner produces a Fitness Function (FF) for classification. The minimized classifier error rate is:

$$fitness(x_i) = ClassifierErrorRate(x_i) = \frac{\text{number of misclassified samples}}{\text{Total number of samples}} * 100 \quad (9)$$

4) Similarity Measurement

The Manhattan distance metric was used for the image retrieval process. Manhattan distance is a metric whereas the distance between 2 points is the total of the absolute variances of Cartesian co-ordinates [20]:

$$d = |p_1 - q_1| + |p_2 - q_2| \quad (10)$$

and the generalization equation to n -dimensional space is expressed as:

$$D_m = \sum_{i=1}^n |p_i - q_i| \quad (11)$$

whereas, n denotes the number of dimensions and p_i, q_i are data points.

5) Image Classification using VAE

At the final stage, the VAE model is utilized for the image classification process. An Auto-Encoder (AE) is an NN which is given the training to try to duplicate its input to output [21]. The Hidden Layer (HL) h defines the code utilized for representing the input. The network could be observed as containing two parts like the encoded function $z = f(x)$ and decoding generates a reconstruction $g(z)$, where x implies the input dataset. One method to attain suitable features in the AE is to make z have lesser dimension than x . The AE code dimension number is lower than the input dimensional and is termed complete. For generating an instance in the method, the VAE primary draws the z instance in the code distribution $p_{model}(z)$. An instance is run over by a differentiable generator network (z). Eventually, x has a distribution $p_{model}(x, g(z)) = p_{model}(x|z)$. In the trained method, the approximate inference network (or encoded) $q(z|x)$ is utilized for obtaining z and $p_{model}(xz)$ is observed as a decoded network. The main insight behind VAEs is that it is trained by maximizing the variational lower bounds $L(q)$ connected to x data points:

$$L(q) = E_{z \sim q(z|x)} \log p_{model}(z, x) + H(q(z|x)) \quad (12)$$

$$= E_{z \sim q(z|x)} \log p_{model}(x|z) - D_{KL}(q(z|x)||p_{model}(z)) \quad (13)$$

Equation (12) distinguishes the first term as the joint log possibility of hidden and visible variables in the estimated hidden variable posterior. If q has a Gaussian distribution with noise and mean value, it maximizes the entropy term and stimulates enhancing the Standard Deviation (SD). Usually, the entropy term stimulates the variational posterior to locate the maximum possibility mass on the z value which is created as x , instead of disintegrating toward a singular point evaluation of probable value. The network defined in (13) is the same. The "reparameterization trick" is used for moving the sample towards the input layers. After computing $p_{model}z = \mu(x) + \theta^{1/2}(x) * e$, its instance in $N(\mu(x), \theta(x))$ by sample $\sim N(0, I)$, $\mu(x)$ and $\theta(x)$ denotes the mean and co-variance of $z|x$. Therefore, (13) is measured as follows:

$$L(q) = E_{\epsilon \sim N(0, I)} p_{model}(x|z = \mu(x) + \theta^{1/2}(x) \times \epsilon) - D_{KL}(q(z|x)||p_{model}(z)) \quad (14)$$

VAE contains multiple AE, input, and output layers. Every AE layer has been trained individually in an unsupervised method, and the outcome of HL in the preceding AE was utilized as input to the subsequent layer. The supervised fine-tuning stage was executed in order to learn the overall parameters of the network utilizing the BP system. This model contains five HLs, one input layer, and one output layer. In Figure 2, the overall confusion matrix of the MRFODL-FIRC method on the DR classification process is illustrated. The outcome shows that the MRFODL-FIRC method gains effectual identification of DR over the existing approaches.

Fig. 2. Confusion matrices of MRFODL-FIRC method (a)-(b) 80:20 and (c)-(d) 70:30 of TRP/TSP.

IV. PERFORMANCE VALIDATION

The suggested technique was simulated by employing Python 3.6.5 on PC i5-8600k, 250GB SSD, GeForce 1050Ti 4GB, 16GB RAM, and 1TB HDD. The parameter set up is: learning rate: 0.01, activation: ReLU, epoch count: 50, dropout: 0.5, and batch size: 5.

The detailed classification output of the MRFODL-FIRC approach on 80:20 of TRP/TSP is shown in Table I. The obtained output infers the effectual identification of different DR stages. As a sample, on 80% of TRP, the MRFODL-FIRC approach obtains an average $accu_y$ of 99.70%, $prec_n$ of 98.12%, $reca_1$ of 98.09%, F_{score} of 98.10%, and AUC_{score} of 98.89%. Alongside, on 20% of TSP, the MRFODL-FIRC methodology attains an average $accu_y$ of 99.78%, $prec_n$ of 98.51%, $reca_1$ of 98.26%, and F_{score} of 98.38%, and AUC_{score} of 99.00%. In Table II, the detailed classification output of the MRFODL-FIRC approach on 70:30 of TRP/TSP is shown. The attained output infers the effectual identification of different DR stages. For instance, on 70% of TRP, the MRFODL-FIRC approach obtains an average $accu_y$ of 98.75%, $prec_n$ of

91.50%, $reca_l$ of 93.12%, F_{score} of 92.24%, and AUC_{score} of 95.93%. On 30% of TSP, the MRFODL-FIRC method obtains an average $accu_y$ of 98.80%, $prec_n$ of 91.68%, $reca_l$ of 93.55%, and F_{score} of 92.50%, and AUC_{score} of 96.15%.

TABLE I. CLASSIFICATION OUTPUT OF MRFODL-FIRC MODEL ON 80:20 OF TRP/TSP

Class	$Accu_y$	$Prec_n$	$Reca_l$	F_{score}	AUC_{score}
Training Phase (80%)					
No DR	99.37	99.62	99.52	99.57	99.24
Mild DR	99.75	97.34	99.08	98.21	99.44
Moderate DR	99.68	98.97	98.94	98.95	99.38
Severe DR	99.83	97.85	95.38	96.60	97.66
Proliferative DR	99.89	96.84	97.53	97.18	98.73
Average	99.70	98.12	98.09	98.10	98.89
Testing Phase (20%)					
No DR	99.47	99.65	99.64	99.64	99.32
Mild DR	99.84	98.16	99.59	98.87	99.72
Moderate DR	99.83	99.52	99.32	99.42	99.62
Severe DR	99.86	98.05	95.57	96.79	97.76
Proliferative DR	99.89	97.18	97.18	97.18	98.56
Average	99.78	98.51	98.26	98.38	99.00

TABLE II. CLASSIFICATION OUTPUT OF MRFODL-FIRC MODEL ON 70:30 OF TRP/TSP

Class	$Accu_y$	$Prec_n$	$Reca_l$	F_{score}	AUC_{score}
Training Phase (70%)					
No DR	97.56	98.57	98.11	98.34	97.07
Mild DR	99.31	95.26	94.58	94.92	97.12
Moderate DR	98.06	92.99	94.15	93.57	96.45
Severe DR	99.44	90.13	87.36	88.72	93.56
Proliferative DR	99.36	80.55	91.41	85.64	95.47
Average	98.75	91.50	93.12	92.24	95.93
Testing Phase (30%)					
No DR	97.57	98.46	98.23	98.34	97.00
Mild DR	99.30	95.51	94.76	95.14	97.21
Moderate DR	98.23	94.24	94.12	94.18	96.54
Severe DR	99.59	93.12	89.84	91.45	94.84
Proliferative DR	99.33	77.06	90.82	83.37	95.15
Average	98.80	91.68	93.55	92.50	96.15

TABLE III. OUTPUT COMPARISON OF THE MRFODL-FIRC MODEL WITH EXISTING APPROACHES

Methods	$Accu_y$	$Prec_n$	$Reca_l$	F_{score}
WFDLN	98.00	95.29	94.70	95.11
AlexNet	89.50	90.87	91.60	91.52
MobileNet	92.90	93.28	93.12	93.46
Xception	92.80	92.33	92.93	92.75
ResNet-50	94.51	95.13	95.33	95.14
MRFODL-FIRC	99.78	98.51	98.26	98.38

Table III demonstrates the comprehensive comparison of the MRFODL-FIRC approach with recent approaches. The results demonstrate the enhanced performance of the MRFODL-FIRC technique with increasing $accu_y$ and F_{score} values. Based on $accu_y$, the MRFODL-FIRC technique reaches an improving $accu_y$ of 99.78% while the AlexNet, MobileNet, Xception, and ResNet-50 approaches obtain lesser $accu_y$ values. The MRFODL-FIRC technique reaches an improved F_{score} of 98.38% while the AlexNet, MobileNet, Xception, and ResNet50 models obtain smaller F_{score} values. These outputs confirm the enhanced achievement of the

MRFODL-FIRC approach over the rest of the currently used methods.

V. CONCLUSION

In this research, an automatic DR grading and classification model, named MRFODL-FIRC is proposed. The presented MRFODL-FIRC technique examined the retinal fundus images efficaciously for retrieving related images and determining classes. It encompasses different sub-processes namely CapsNet-based feature extraction, MF-based pre-processing, MRFO-based tuning process, Manhattan distance-based similarity measuring, and VAE classification. The experimental assessment of the MRFODL-FIRC technique was conducted on a medical DR dataset and the outputs highlighted the improved performance of the MRFODL-FIRC technique over the currently used techniques. Therefore, the presented MRFODL-FIRC technique is useful for effectual retrieving and classification of retinal images. In the future, the MRFODL-FIRC method can be boosted by a deep instance segmenting process. Besides, the computation complexity of the proposed model needs to be investigated.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. K. Singh, M. Khanna, S. Thawkar, and R. Singh, "Collaboration of features optimization techniques for the effective diagnosis of glaucoma in retinal fundus images," *Advances in Engineering Software*, vol. 173, Nov. 2022, Art. no. 103283, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.advengsoft.2022.103283>.
- [2] G. Kalyani, B. Janakiramaiah, A. Karuna, and L. V. N. Prasad, "Diabetic retinopathy detection and classification using capsule networks," *Complex & Intelligent Systems*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 2651–2664, Jun. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40747-021-00318-9>.
- [3] M. Sahoo, S. Ghorai, M. Mitra, and S. Pal, "Improved detection accuracy of red lesions in retinal fundus images with superlearning approach," *Photodiagnosis and Photodynamic Therapy*, vol. 42, Jun. 2023, Art. no. 103351, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pdpdt.2023.103351>.
- [4] G. Saxena, D. K. Verma, A. Paraye, A. Rajan, and A. Rawat, "Improved and robust deep learning agent for preliminary detection of diabetic retinopathy using public datasets," *Intelligence-Based Medicine*, vol. 3–4, Dec. 2020, Art. no. 100022, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ibmed.2020.100022>.
- [5] M. S. Farooq *et al.*, "Untangling Computer-Aided Diagnostic System for Screening Diabetic Retinopathy Based on Deep Learning Techniques," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 5, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 1803, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22051803>.
- [6] H. Fu *et al.*, "A Deep Learning System for Automated Angle-Closure Detection in Anterior Segment Optical Coherence Tomography Images," *American Journal of Ophthalmology*, vol. 203, pp. 37–45, Jul. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajo.2019.02.028>.
- [7] V. D. Vinayaki and R. Kalaiselvi, "Multithreshold Image Segmentation Technique Using Remora Optimization Algorithm for Diabetic Retinopathy Detection from Fundus Images," *Neural Processing Letters*, vol. 54, no. 3, pp. 2363–2384, Jun. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11063-021-10734-0>.
- [8] K. Aldriwish, "A Deep Learning Approach for Malware and Software Piracy Threat Detection," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 7757–7762, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4412>.
- [9] N. B. Serradj, A. D. K. Ali, and M. E. A. Ghernaout, "A Contribution to the Thermal Field Evaluation at the Tool-Part Interface for the Optimization of Machining Conditions," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 7750–7756, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4235>.
- [10] S. Nuanmeesri, "A Hybrid Deep Learning and Optimized Machine Learning Approach for Rose Leaf Disease Classification," *Engineering,*

- Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7678–7683, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4455>.
- [11] P. K. Jena, B. Khuntia, C. Palai, M. Nayak, T. K. Mishra, and S. N. Mohanty, "A Novel Approach for Diabetic Retinopathy Screening Using Asymmetric Deep Learning Features," *Big Data and Cognitive Computing*, vol. 7, no. 1, Mar. 2023, Art. no. 25, <https://doi.org/10.3390/bdcc7010025>.
- [12] M. R. Islam *et al.*, "Applying supervised contrastive learning for the detection of diabetic retinopathy and its severity levels from fundus images," *Computers in Biology and Medicine*, vol. 146, Jul. 2022, Art. no. 105602, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compbiomed.2022.105602>.
- [13] A. Bilal, L. Zhu, A. Deng, H. Lu, and N. Wu, "AI-Based Automatic Detection and Classification of Diabetic Retinopathy Using U-Net and Deep Learning," *Symmetry*, vol. 14, no. 7, Jul. 2022, Art. no. 1427, <https://doi.org/10.3390/sym14071427>.
- [14] E. Abdelmaksoud, S. El-Sappagh, S. Barakat, T. Abuhmed, and M. Elmogy, "Automatic Diabetic Retinopathy Grading System Based on Detecting Multiple Retinal Lesions," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 15939–15960, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3052870>.
- [15] M. T. Al-Antary and Y. Arafa, "Multi-Scale Attention Network for Diabetic Retinopathy Classification," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 54190–54200, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3070685>.
- [16] S. Maqsood, R. Damaševičius, and R. Maskeliūnas, "Hemorrhage Detection Based on 3D CNN Deep Learning Framework and Feature Fusion for Evaluating Retinal Abnormality in Diabetic Patients," *Sensors (Basel, Switzerland)*, vol. 21, no. 11, Jun. 2021, Art. no. 3865, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s21113865>.
- [17] A. Noor, Y. Zhao, R. Khan, L. Wu, and F. Y. O. Abdalla, "Median filters combined with denoising convolutional neural network for Gaussian and impulse noises," *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, vol. 79, no. 25, pp. 18553–18568, Jul. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-020-08657-4>.
- [18] A. Moudgil, S. Singh, V. Gautam, S. Rani, and S. H. Shah, "Handwritten devanagari manuscript characters recognition using capsnet," *International Journal of Cognitive Computing in Engineering*, vol. 4, pp. 47–54, Jun. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijcce.2023.02.001>.
- [19] A. Moudgil, S. Singh, V. Gautam, S. Rani, and S. H. Shah, "Handwritten devanagari manuscript characters recognition using capsnet," *International Journal of Cognitive Computing in Engineering*, vol. 4, pp. 47–54, Jun. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijcce.2023.02.001>.
- [20] N. E. M. Isa, A. Amir, M. Z. Ilyas, and M. S. Razalli, "The Performance Analysis of K-Nearest Neighbors (K-NN) Algorithm for Motor Imagery Classification Based on EEG Signal," *MATEC Web of Conferences*, vol. 140, 2017, Art. no. 01024, <https://doi.org/10.1051/mateconf/201714001024>.
- [21] M. Dai, D. Zheng, R. Na, S. Wang, and S. Zhang, "EEG Classification of Motor Imagery Using a Novel Deep Learning Framework," *Sensors (Basel, Switzerland)*, vol. 19, no. 3, Jan. 2019, Art. no. 551, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s19030551>.

Nonsingular Fast Terminal Sliding Mode Controller for a Robotic System: A Fuzzy Approach

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ABSTRACT

This study presents a combination of Type-2 fuzzy logic and nonsingular fast sliding mode technique to design a robust controller for a robotic system. The control law is composed of two signals. The first one called equivalent control law is dedicated to maintaining the system on the sliding surface and then converges to zero. Since the system is uncertain, a Type-2 fuzzy nominal model was constructed, deduced from linear local models, which allows a good approximation of the real robotic system. The second signal, whose objective is to force the system to attain the sliding surface, is deduced from stability analysis using Lyapunov theory. Several simulations were conducted to evaluate the efficiency of the proposed approach, showing good tracking performance for different reference signals despite the presence of uncertainties and external disturbances.

Keywords-robotic system; nonsingular fast terminal sliding mode control

I. INTRODUCTION

Sliding mode control is a very popular approach to ensure good tracking performance against external disturbances [1-5]. Despite its simple design procedure and good tracking performance, it has two major disadvantages. The first one is the chattering phenomenon introduced by using the signum function in the control signal. The second disadvantage lies in its time convergence, which cannot be imposed. Several improvements have been proposed to reduce chattering phenomena [1, 6-8]. However, these methods need a trade-off between the smoothness of the switching signal and tracking performance. Second-order sliding mode control has presented a good solution to chattering, but the design procedure is complex and requires a good knowledge of the studied system [9]. Recently, terminal sliding mode control was proposed, where a nonlinear surface is used to guarantee a finite time convergence to the origin of the phase plan. However, these types of controllers suffer from the singularity problem due to the presence of terms with negative fractional powers [10-12]. This problem can be resolved by using a nonsingular terminal sliding mode controller [13]. Nevertheless, this improvement was obtained at the expense of the convergence time, which became slower. A nonsingular fast terminal sliding mode controller was developed to overcome singularity and obtain a fast convergence time [14]. This paper proposes a Type-2 fuzzy nonsingular fast terminal sliding mode controller for a robotic system, guaranteeing finite-time convergence, fast speed when the states are far from the origin, avoidance of singularity, and no chattering. The design procedure consists of two major steps. In the first step, a nominal model was designed using a

Type-2 fuzzy system, exploiting linear local models, which allows the construction of a nominal model too close to the real system. This model was used to design the equivalent control law, whose mission is to maintain the system on the sliding surface and slide on to zero. The second step aimed to establish the switching signal on the sliding surface despite the presence of external disturbances and uncertainties.

II. INTERVAL TYPE-2 FUZZY LOGIC SYSTEMS

Fuzzy logic systems are known as universal approximators and have several applications in control design and identification. A Type-1 Fuzzy Logic System (T1FLS) consists of four major parts: fuzzifier, rule base, inference engine, and defuzzifier. A Type-2 Fuzzy Logic System (T2FLS) is very similar to a T1FLS [15-16], and the major structure difference is that the defuzzifier block of a T1FLS is replaced by the output processing block, which consists of type-reduction followed by defuzzification. In an interval T2FLS, a triangular fuzzy set is defined by a lower and upper set, as shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 1. Structure of a T2FLS.

Fig. 2. Interval T2FLS sets.

It is clear that the interval Type-2 fuzzy set is in a region bounded by an upper and a lower membership function, denoted as $\bar{\mu}_{\tilde{A}}(x)$ and $\underline{\mu}_{\tilde{A}}$, respectively, and is named as Foot of Uncertainty (FOU). Assuming that there are M rules in a Type-2 fuzzy rule base, each of them has the following form:

$$R^i: \text{IF } x_1 \text{ is } \tilde{F}_1^i \text{ and } \dots \text{ and } x_n \text{ is } \tilde{F}_n^i \text{ THEN } y \text{ is } [w_l^i \ w_r^i]$$

where $x_j, j = 1, 2, \dots, n$, and y are the input and output variables of the T2FLS, respectively, \tilde{F}_j^i is the Type 2 fuzzy sets of antecedent part, and $[w_l^i \ w_r^i]$ is the weighting interval set in the consequent part. The operation of type-reduction is to give a Type-1 set from a Type-2 set. In the meantime, the firing strength F^i for the i -th rule can be an interval Type-2 set expressed as:

$$F^i \equiv [\underline{f}^i, \bar{f}^i]$$

where:

$$\begin{cases} \underline{f}^i = \underline{\mu}_{\tilde{F}_1^i}(x_1) * \dots * \underline{\mu}_{\tilde{F}_n^i}(x_n) \\ \bar{f}^i = \bar{\mu}_{\tilde{F}_1^i}(x_1) * \dots * \bar{\mu}_{\tilde{F}_n^i}(x_n) \end{cases}$$

This study used the center of the set type-reduction method to simplify the notation. Therefore, the output can be expressed as:

$$y_{cos}(x) = [y_l ; y_r]$$

where $y_{cos}(x)$ is also an interval Type-1 set determined by the left and right-most points (y_l and y_r), which can be derived from the consequent centroid set $[w_l^i \ w_r^i]$ (either \underline{w}^i or \bar{w}^i) and the firing strength $f^i \in F^i \equiv [\underline{f}^i, \bar{f}^i]$. The interval set $[w_l^i \ w_r^i]$ ($i = 1, \dots, M$) should be computed or set before the computation of $y_{cos}(x)$. Therefore, the left-most point y_l and the right-most point y_r can be expressed as [17]:

$$\begin{cases} y_l = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^M \underline{f}^i w_l^i}{\sum_{i=1}^M \underline{f}^i} \\ y_r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^M \bar{f}^i w_r^i}{\sum_{i=1}^M \bar{f}^i} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Using the center of set type reduction method to compute y_l and y_r the defuzzified crisp output from an interval T2FLS can be obtained according to:

$$y(x) = \frac{y_l + y_r}{2} \quad (2)$$

which can be rewritten in the following vectorial form:

$$y(x) = \Psi^T(x) \cdot w \quad (3)$$

where $\Psi^T(x)$ represents the regressive vector and w the consequent vector containing the conclusion values of the fuzzy rules.

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Let's consider the dynamic equation of n Degree-of-Freedom (DoF) robotic manipulators as follows:

$$M(q)\ddot{q} + C(q, \dot{q})\dot{q} + G(q, \dot{q}) = \Gamma(t) + \Gamma_{ext}(t) \quad (4)$$

where q, \dot{q} and $\ddot{q} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ are the vector of joint position, joint velocity, and joint acceleration, respectively, $M(q) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is a symmetric and positive definite inertia matrix, $C(q, \dot{q}) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is the matrix of centrifugal and Coriolis forces, $G(q) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the vector of gravitational forces, $\Gamma(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the vector of input joint torque, and $\Gamma_{ext}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the vector of unknown external disturbances.

Fig. 3. Two link robot manipulators (2 DoFs).

For practical applications, it is impossible to know the exact dynamic model of the robotic manipulators. Therefore, the above dynamic quantities can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} M(q) &= M_0(q) + \Delta M(q) \\ C(q, \dot{q}) &= C_0(q, \dot{q}) + \Delta C(q, \dot{q}) \\ G(q) &= G_0(q) + \Delta G(q) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $M_0(q)$, $C_0(q, \dot{q})$, and $G_0(q)$ are the nominal values and $\Delta M(q)$, $\Delta C(q, \dot{q})$, $\Delta G(q)$ are the uncertain parts of $M(q)$, $C(q, \dot{q})$, and $G(q)$, respectively. Using (5), the dynamic model of the robotic manipulators can be expressed as:

$$M_0(q)\ddot{q} + C_0(q, \dot{q})\dot{q} + G_0(q, \dot{q}) = \Gamma(t) + \delta(q, \dot{q}, \ddot{q}) \quad (6)$$

where:

$$\delta(q, \dot{q}, \ddot{q}) = \Gamma_{ext}(t) - \Delta M(q)\ddot{q} - \Delta C(q, \dot{q})\dot{q} - \Delta G(q)$$

Let's define the tracking error $e = q - q_d$ and its time derivative $\dot{e} = \dot{q} - \dot{q}_d$ where q_d is the desired trajectory. The error dynamic of the robotic manipulators with the uncertainties and disturbances can be written as:

$$\ddot{e} = f(e, \dot{e}) + g(e, \dot{e})\Gamma(t) + D(e, \dot{e}) \quad (7)$$

where:

$$f(e, \dot{e}) = -M_0^{-1}(q)[C_0(q, \dot{q})\dot{q} + G_0(q, \dot{q})] - \ddot{q}_d$$

$$g(e, \dot{e}) = M_0^{-1}(q) \text{ and } D(e, \dot{e}) = M_0^{-1}(q) \delta(q, \dot{q}, \ddot{q})$$

As given in [13], the upper bound of lumped uncertainty can be expressed as:

$$|D(e, \dot{e})| \leq a_0 + a_1|q| + a_2|\dot{q}|^2 \quad (8)$$

where a_0 , a_1 and a_2 are positive scalars. The next task is to develop a robust controller based on Nonsingular Fast Terminal Sliding Mode Control (NFTSMC) allowing tracking objectives.

IV. CONTROLLER DESIGN

To design the controller, let's consider the following nonsingular terminal sliding surface:

$$S(t) = e + k_1|e|^\alpha \text{sign}(e) + k_2|\dot{e}|^\beta \text{sign}(\dot{e}) \quad (9)$$

where k_1 and k_2 are positive constants, and:

$$1 < \beta < 2 \text{ and } \alpha > \beta$$

The structure of this surface allows to attain fast convergence of the tracking error to zero. If the position's initial value is far from the desired one, then the term $k_1|e|^\alpha \text{sign}(e)$ will be dominant, leading to fast convergence. In the case where the system is near the desired trajectory, the term $k_2|\dot{e}|^\beta \text{sign}(\dot{e})$ must ensure a finite time convergence. The time derivative of the sliding surface can be written as:

$$\dot{S}(t) = \dot{e} + \alpha \cdot k_1|e|^{\alpha-1} \dot{e} + \beta \cdot k_2|\dot{e}|^{\beta-1} \ddot{e} \quad (10)$$

The control law is composed of two terms. The first one, named equivalent control $\Gamma_e(t)$, is dedicated to maintaining the system on the sliding surface. The second term $\Gamma_s(t)$, called the switching signal, must force the system to converge to the sliding surface. Then, to design the equivalent control law $\Gamma_e(t)$, it is considered that the system is on the surface ($S(t) = 0$) and remains on ($\dot{S}(t) = 0$). In this case, the system is considered insensitive to uncertainties and external disturbances [1]. Using (7), (10) can be rewritten as:

$$\dot{S}(t) = \dot{e} + \alpha \cdot k_1|e|^{\alpha-1} \dot{e} + \beta \cdot k_2|\dot{e}|^{\beta-1} \cdot [f(e, \dot{e}) + g(e, \dot{e})\Gamma_e(t)] \quad (11)$$

The equivalent control law can be expressed as:

$$\Gamma_e(t) = -g^{-1}(e, \dot{e}) \cdot [f(e, \dot{e}) + [\beta \cdot k_2]^{-1} |\dot{e}|^{2-\beta} (1 + \alpha \cdot k_1|e|^{\alpha-1}) \text{sign}(\dot{e})] \quad (12)$$

Note that, $\dot{e} = |\dot{e}| \cdot \text{sign}(\dot{e})$ was used to write (9) in a compact form. The next task is to determine the expression of the switching signal $\Gamma_s(t)$ allowing to force the system to reach the sliding surface in the presence of uncertainties and external disturbances. In this case, (10) becomes:

$$\dot{S}(t) = \dot{e} + \alpha \cdot k_1|e|^{\alpha-1} \dot{e} + \beta \cdot k_2|\dot{e}|^{\beta-1} \cdot [f(e, \dot{e}) + g(e, \dot{e})\Gamma(t) + D(e, \dot{e})] \quad (13)$$

Using (12), (10) can be rewritten as:

$$\dot{S}(t) = \dot{e} + \alpha \cdot k_1|e|^{\alpha-1} \dot{e} + \beta \cdot k_2|\dot{e}|^{\beta-1} \cdot [f(e, \dot{e}) + g(e, \dot{e})\Gamma_e(t) + \beta \cdot k_2|\dot{e}|^{\beta-1} \cdot [g(e, \dot{e})\Gamma_s(t) + D(e, \dot{e})]] \quad (14)$$

According to the definition of the equivalent control, (14) can be simplified to:

$$\dot{S}(t) = \beta \cdot k_2|\dot{e}|^{\beta-1} \cdot [g(e, \dot{e})\Gamma_s(t) + D(e, \dot{e})] \quad (15)$$

To deduce the expression of $\Gamma_s(t)$ allowing the switching condition, the following Lyapunov function was considered:

$$V(t) = \frac{1}{2}S^2(t) \quad (16)$$

Differentiating $V(t)$ for time and using (15) lead to:

$$\dot{V}(t) = S(t) \cdot \beta \cdot k_2|\dot{e}|^{\beta-1} \cdot [g(e, \dot{e})\Gamma_s(t) + D(e, \dot{e})] \quad (17)$$

Choosing $\Gamma_s(t)$ as:

$$\Gamma_s(t) = -g^{-1}(e, \dot{e})[k_{01} \cdot S(t) + (k_{02} + a_0 + a_1|q| + a_2|\dot{q}|^2) \cdot \text{sign}(S(t))] \quad (18)$$

where k_{01} and k_{02} are two positive scalars.

The time derivative of the Lyapunov function becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}(t) &= S(t) \beta \cdot k_2|\dot{e}|^{\beta-1} \cdot [g(e, \dot{e})\Gamma_s(t) + D(e, \dot{e})] \\ &= \beta \cdot k_2|\dot{e}|^{\beta-1} \cdot [-k_{01} \cdot S^2(t) - (k_{02} + a_0 + a_1|q| + a_2|\dot{q}|^2) \cdot |S(t)| + D(e, \dot{e})] \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Using the assumption (8), the following inequality is obtained:

$$\dot{V}(t) \leq \beta \cdot k_2|\dot{e}|^{\beta-1} \cdot [-k_{01} \cdot S^2(t) - k_{02} \cdot |S(t)|] \leq 0 \quad (20)$$

Based on the Lyapunov theorem, the system converges asymptotically to the sliding surface and remains on. To prove convergence in finite time, let's take up inequality (20):

$$\dot{V}(t) \leq -\beta \cdot k_{01} \cdot k_2|\dot{e}|^{\beta-1} \cdot S^2(t) - \beta \cdot k_{02} \cdot k_2|\dot{e}|^{\beta-1} \cdot |S(t)| \quad (21)$$

$$\dot{V}(t) \leq -\frac{2\beta k_{01} \cdot k_2|\dot{e}|^{\beta-1}}{\beta_1} \cdot V(t) - \frac{\sqrt{2}\beta k_{02} \cdot k_2|\dot{e}|^{\beta-1}}{\beta_2} \cdot V^{\frac{1}{2}}(t) \quad (22)$$

and then:

$$dt \leq \frac{-dV(t)}{\beta_1 \cdot V(t) + \beta_2 \cdot V^{\frac{1}{2}}(t)} = -2 \cdot \frac{dV^{\frac{1}{2}}(t)}{\beta_1 \cdot V^{\frac{1}{2}}(t) + \beta_2} \quad (23)$$

Integrating inequality (23) and after some mathematical manipulation, the following can be obtained:

$$t_c \leq \frac{2}{\beta_1} \ln \left(\frac{\beta_1 \cdot V^{\frac{1}{2}}(0) + \beta_2}{\beta_2} \right)$$

It can be concluded that the time convergence to zero is finite.

V. SIMULATION AND RESULTS

To evaluate the performance of the proposed approach, a two-link robot was considered, as shown in Figure 3, whose dynamics equation is given by [14]:

$$\begin{bmatrix} M_{11}(q) & M_{12}(q) \\ M_{21}(q) & M_{22}(q) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \ddot{q}_1 \\ \ddot{q}_2 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} C_{11}(q, \dot{q}) & C_{12}(q, \dot{q}) \\ C_{21}(q, \dot{q}) & C_{22}(q, \dot{q}) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{q}_1 \\ \dot{q}_2 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} G_1(q) \\ G_2(q) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \Gamma_1(t) \\ \Gamma_2(t) \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \Gamma_{ext1}(t) \\ \Gamma_{ext2}(t) \end{bmatrix}$$

where:

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_{11}(q) &= (m_1 + m_2)l_1^2 \\
 M_{12}(q) &= M_{21}(q) = m_2l_1l_2(\sin(q_1)\sin(q_2) + \cos(q_1)\cos(q_2)) \\
 M_{22}(q) &= m_2l_2^2 \\
 C_{11}(q, \dot{q}) &= -m_2l_1l_2(\cos(q_1)\sin(q_2) - \sin(q_1)\cos(q_2))\dot{q}_2 \\
 C_{21}(q, \dot{q}) &= -m_2l_1l_2(\cos(q_1)\sin(q_2) - \sin(q_1)\cos(q_2))\dot{q}_1 \\
 C_{11}(q, \dot{q}) &= C_{22}(q, \dot{q}) = 0 \\
 G_1(q) &= -(m_1 + m_2)l_1g \cdot \sin(q_1) \\
 G_2(q) &= -m_2l_2g \cdot \sin(q_2) \\
 m_1 &= m_2 = 1Kg; l_1 = l_2 = 1m; g = 9.8ms^{-2}
 \end{aligned}$$

To construct the Type 2 fuzzy nominal model, the positions q_1 and q_2 were considered to be constrained within $[-\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2}]$, which leads to nine fuzzy rules. Each of them gives the relation between the equilibrium point and the corresponding local model. Then, each rule uses a Type-2 fuzzy set in the antecedent part to describe the equilibrium point and the consequent part of the corresponding local model. Using the product as an interference engine, the center set for the reduction type, and the center of gravity for defuzzification, the output fuzzy system will give the Type-2 fuzzy nominal model. Figures 4 to 6 show the results obtained for sinusoidal reference trajectories ($q_{1d}(t)=\sin(t)$, $q_{2d}(t)=\cos(t)$) and the system subjected to both uncertainties (10% of nominal values of the system) and external disturbances in the form:

$$\Gamma_{ext}(t) = 0.2 \sin(t) + 0.1\sin(2t)$$

Figure 7 shows another reference trajectory considered to demonstrate the performance of the proposed approach. This case also demonstrates the convergence of the system outputs towards the reference trajectories, confirming the previous conclusion.

Fig. 4. Angular position tracking.

Fig. 5. Angular position tracking error.

Fig. 6. Applied control signals.

Fig. 7. Angular position tracking.

To further demonstrate the performance of the proposed approach, a comparative study was conducted with a Fuzzy Sliding Mode Control (FSMC) [2] and a Terminal Sliding Mode Controller (TSMC) [18] in terms of the Mean Square value of the Tracking Error (MSTE) defined as:

$$e_i = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \|e_i(k)\|^2}, i = 1, 2$$

Table I shows the obtained MSTE values after using each method. As can be seen, the proposed approach obtained a smaller MSTE, demonstrating its better performance than the two other control methods.

TABLE I. MSTE VALUES

	Joint 1 (rad)	Joint 2 (rad)
FSMC	0.045	0.06
TSMC	0.04	0.055
Proposed method	0.025	0.035

Thus, it can be concluded that the proposed approach ensures high tracking precision, fast response, singularity avoidance, and strong robustness to external disturbances and modeling uncertainties.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study proposed a Type-2 fuzzy nonsingular fast terminal sliding mode controller for a robotic system. In the first step, the equivalent control law was elaborated based on a Type-2 fuzzy nominal model, which allows a good approximation of the real robotic system. This made it possible to effectively exploit human expertise in the behavior of the system, the flexibility of Type-2 fuzzy logic, and its ability to better consider uncertainties compared to other classical modeling methods. In the second step, Lyapunov theory was used to study the stability of the closed-loop system and deduce the expression of the switching signal. The designed control law, composed of two terms, was mathematically proven to lead to robustness against uncertainties and external disturbances, in addition to its convergence to the reference trajectories in a finite time. To demonstrate the performance of the proposed approach in terms of robustness and tracking, a simulation was conducted for sinusoidal trajectories with different initial positions and square reference signals. The results and the comparative study with other approaches demonstrated the superiority of the proposed approach in terms of MSTE. In the future, the implementation of this approach will be simplified by reducing the number of parameters and simplifying the expression of the switching signal.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. J. E. Slotine and W. Li, *Applied Nonlinear Control*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ, USA: Prentice Hall, 1991.
- [2] A. Hamzaoui, N. Essounbouli, and J. Zaytoon, "Fuzzy sliding mode control with a fuzzy switching function for non-linear uncertain multi-input multi-output systems," *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part I: Journal of Systems and Control Engineering*, vol. 218, no. 4, pp. 287–297, Jun. 2004, <https://doi.org/10.1177/095965180421800404>.
- [3] M. Boukattaya, N. Mezghani, and T. Damak, "Adaptive nonsingular fast terminal sliding-mode control for the tracking problem of uncertain dynamical systems," *ISA Transactions*, vol. 77, pp. 1–19, Jun. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isatra.2018.04.007>.
- [4] Y. Pan, C. Yang, L. Pan, and H. Yu, "Integral Sliding Mode Control: Performance, Modification, and Improvement," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 14, no. 7, pp. 3087–3096, Jul. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TII.2017.2761389>.
- [5] S. Ullah, Q. Khan, A. Mehmood, and A. I. Bhatti, "Robust Backstepping Sliding Mode Control Design for a Class of Underactuated Electro-Mechanical Nonlinear Systems," *Journal of Electrical Engineering & Technology*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 1821–1828, Jul. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42835-020-00436-3>.
- [6] S. Ahmad, A. A. Uppal, M. R. Azam, and J. Iqbal, "Chattering Free Sliding Mode Control and State Dependent Kalman Filter Design for Underground Gasification Energy Conversion Process," *Electronics*, vol. 12, no. 4, Jan. 2023, Art. no. 876, <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics12040876>.
- [7] L. Wan, G. Chen, M. Sheng, Y. Zhang, and Z. Zhang, "Adaptive chattering-free terminal sliding-mode control for full-order nonlinear system with unknown disturbances and model uncertainties," *International Journal of Advanced Robotic Systems*, vol. 17, no. 3, May 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1177/1729881420925295>.
- [8] A. T. Vo and H.-J. Kang, "A Chattering-Free, Adaptive, Robust Tracking Control Scheme for Nonlinear Systems With Uncertain Dynamics," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 10457–10466, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2891763>.
- [9] M. Manceur, N. Essounbouli, and A. Hamzaoui, "Second-Order Sliding Fuzzy Interval Type-2 Control for an Uncertain System With Real Application," *IEEE Transactions on Fuzzy Systems*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 262–275, Apr. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TFUZZ.2011.2172948>.
- [10] T. N. Truong, A. T. Vo, and H.-J. Kang, "A Backstepping Global Fast Terminal Sliding Mode Control for Trajectory Tracking Control of Industrial Robotic Manipulators," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 31921–31931, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3060115>.
- [11] M. Van, S. S. Ge, and H. Ren, "Finite Time Fault Tolerant Control for Robot Manipulators Using Time Delay Estimation and Continuous Nonsingular Fast Terminal Sliding Mode Control," *IEEE Transactions on Cybernetics*, vol. 47, no. 7, pp. 1681–1693, Jul. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCYB.2016.2555307>.
- [12] A. Ferrara and G. P. Incremona, "Design of an Integral Suboptimal Second-Order Sliding Mode Controller for the Robust Motion Control of Robot Manipulators," *IEEE Transactions on Control Systems Technology*, vol. 23, no. 6, pp. 2316–2325, Aug. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCST.2015.2420624>.
- [13] X. Liang, H. Wang, and Y. Zhang, "Adaptive nonsingular terminal sliding mode control for rehabilitation robots," *Computers and Electrical Engineering*, vol. 99, Art. no. 107718, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compeleceng.2022.107718>.
- [14] L. Alnufaie, "Nonsingular Fast Terminal Sliding Mode Controller for a Robotic System: A Fuzzy Approach," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 75522–75527, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3288000>.
- [15] A. Al-Mahturi, F. Santoso, M. A. Garratt, and S. G. Anavatti, "A Novel Evolving Type-2 Fuzzy System for Controlling a Mobile Robot under Large Uncertainties," *Robotics*, vol. 12, no. 2, Apr. 2023, Art. no. 40, <https://doi.org/10.3390/robotics12020040>.
- [16] N. N. Karnik, J. M. Mendel, and Q. Liang, "Type-2 fuzzy logic systems," *IEEE Transactions on Fuzzy Systems*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 643–658, Sep. 1999, <https://doi.org/10.1109/91.811231>.
- [17] M. Manceur, L. Menhour, N. Essounbouli, and A. Hamzaoui, "MIMO sliding fuzzy type-2 control with manipulating approaching phase," in *2013 10th IEEE International Conference on Networking, Sensing and Control (ICNSC)*, Evry, France, Apr. 2013, pp. 479–485, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICNSC.2013.6548786>.
- [18] V. Utkin, A. Poznyak, Y. Orlov, and A. Polyakov, "Conventional and high order sliding mode control," *Journal of the Franklin Institute*, vol. 357, no. 15, pp. 10244–10261, Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfranklin.2020.06.018>.

Surface Roughness in Metal Material Extrusion 3D Printing: The Influence of Printing Orientation and the Development of a Predictive Model

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the influence of printing orientation on the surface roughness in metal material extrusion 3D printing of 17-4 PH stainless steel. Experimental tests were conducted on the Markforged Metal X commercial 3D printer at Vinh Long University of Technology Education, Vietnam. The samples were printed in three different orientations: flat, on-edge, and upright. Surface roughness measurements were performed using a handheld Mitutoyo SJ-210 roughness tester. Quantitative analysis of the surface roughness measurements revealed significant variations among the different printing orientations. The upright orientation exhibited the smoothest surface, with an average R_a value of 7.42 μm and R_z value of 40.49 μm . In contrast, the flat orientation showed the highest roughness, with an average R_a value of 82.83 μm and R_z value of 109.32 μm . The on-edge orientation had intermediate roughness values, with an average R_a value of 69.42 μm and R_z value of 92.17 μm . The study also introduces a novel predictive model for surface roughness based on the printing parameters. The model demonstrated accurate estimations for surface roughness values in specific cases, enabling optimization of the printing process for desired surface quality.

Keywords-additive manufacturing; material extrusion; 17-4 PH stainless steel; building orientation; microstructure; mechanical properties

I. INTRODUCTION

Additive Manufacturing (AM) or 3D printing is a production process that allows the creation of products by adding material layer by layer to form detailed components from a 3D digital model [1-4]. The ASTM/ISO standards classify metal 3D printing technologies into 7 different groups: Material Extrusion (ME), Material Jetting (MJ), Binder Jetting (BJ), VAT photopolymerization, Powder Bed Fusion (PBF),

Direct Energy Deposition (DED), and sheet object lamination (ASTM ISO/ASTM52900-15, 2015). ME technology accounted for 10% of the metal 3D printing market in 2020 [5]. The fundamental characteristic of ME printing technology is the extrusion of material layer by layer through a print head to form 3D components. Unlike metal powder-based printing processes, ME printing technology involves extruding materials in the form of filaments. These filaments are flexible materials made from a mixture of metal powder and binding

agents [6, 7]. ME printing technology is used to print the components as shown in Figure 1. The ME printing machine consists of two spools, one containing the printing material and the other containing ceramic material used to print the separators between the product and the build plate or between the product and support structures. During printing, the print head heats the printing material above the melting temperature of the polymer binder, extruding the softened material onto the build plate. The print head moves up and down along the vertical z-axis, extruding each layer of material evenly. Simultaneously, the build plate moves in the x-y direction, shaping the form of the component. The ceramic material is printed as a barrier between the component and support structures or as a separation layer between the component and the build plate to facilitate easy removal of the product after the sintering process. The printing nozzle extrudes filaments with circular cross-sections, layer by layer. There are gaps between the layers, which reduce adhesion between the metal layers and can cause deformation during the sintering process in Figure 2.

Fig. 1. The Markforged Metal X 3D printer used for experimental printing.

Fig. 2. Printing process and the gaps between the printed layers.

Fig. 3. The voids between deposits of the product before sintering

The as-printed or "green" part undergoes a debinding process known as "washing." The delicate and loosely bound workpiece is placed inside a heated debinding machine, where a solvent is used to dissolve a portion of the core component of the binder system. The binder system plays a significant role in influencing the production process and the quality of the final component. Typically, it consists of three main components: polymers, waxes, and additives. It can be further classified into the core, the backbone, and the additive. The core component constitutes 50-90% of the volume and includes materials with low viscosity that are easily dissolved and can undergo catalytic degradation. These materials are effectively removed during the initial debinding stage. The backbone component accounts for 0-50% of the volume and consists of materials that are resistant to debinding solvents. This component helps maintain the strength of the debound part before sintering, such as polyolefins. The final additive can make up 0-10% of the volume of the binder system. The core component is gradually dissolved, leaving behind the backbone, which is referred to as being in its "brown" state. The brown part retains much of the backbone but remains highly porous. Subsequently, the part is placed into a furnace and subjected to a gradual increase in temperature from ambient to 70-90% of the metal's melting point. This thermal process decomposes the residual support component of the binder system. As the temperature rises within the furnace, solid bonds or necks start to form between the metal powder particles, thereby reducing the surface energy of the part. Upon reaching the metal's melting point, atomic diffusion of the metal particles occurs, leading to the formation of solid bonds. This reduces porosity and transforms the loosely bound metal powder into a theoretically dense metal part with a density of 96-99.8%. This densification process results in shrinkage of the part by 12-20%, which is taken into account by the system's software during the file transfer stage [8].

The surface quality of metal 3D printing is assessed through various parameters, including hardness, residual stress on the surface layer, and surface roughness. Among these parameters, surface roughness plays a significant role in the performance and lifespan of the machine component and is often chosen as a key evaluation criterion in production processes. Surface roughness is evaluated based on the profile of the surface texture formed between the intersection of the actual surface of the component and a plane perpendicular to the actual surface. Two parameters, average roughness (R_a) and peak-to-valley height (R_z), are used to draw conclusions [9, 10]. Specialized surface roughness measuring devices are used to determine the surface roughness of the component. It is typically measured in micrometers (μm) or microinches (μin). High surface roughness can result in increased friction, reduced component durability, and decreased dimensional accuracy. The effects of printing parameters on surface roughness in the Metal Additive Manufacturing (MAM) have been studied by various authors. For example, authors in [11] considered the effect of printing orientation on the surface roughness and microstructure in selective laser melting of Ti-6Al-4V. This study investigates the effect of print orientation on surface roughness and microstructure in the selective laser melting of Ti-6Al-4V. The authors found that print orientation has a significant impact on

surface roughness, with parts printed vertically exhibiting higher roughness than those printed horizontally. The microstructure of the printed parts was also found to be orientation-dependent. This study provides important insights for optimizing the selective laser melting process for Ti-6Al-4V. Authors in [12] investigated the influence of building orientation on surface roughness in the selective laser melting of Inconel 718. They found that print orientation has a significant impact on surface roughness, with parts printed vertically exhibiting higher roughness than those printed horizontally. The authors suggest that this is due to differences in cooling rates and thermal gradients during the printing process. This study provides important insights for optimizing the selective laser melting process for Inconel 718. Authors in [13] found that print orientation has a significant impact on surface quality and mechanical properties, with parts printed horizontally exhibiting better surface quality and higher mechanical properties than those printed vertically. This study provides important insights for optimizing the electron beam melting process for Ti-6Al-4V. Authors in [14] investigated the relationship between the surface roughness and the mechanical properties in the selective laser melting of stainless steel. They found that print orientation has a significant impact on both surface roughness and mechanical properties, with parts printed vertically exhibiting higher roughness and lower mechanical properties than those printed horizontally. This study provides important insight for optimizing the selective laser melting process for stainless steel.

The aim of the present paper is to introduce a novel geometrical model for the prediction of surface roughness in lateral walls within the context of ME printing. This model takes into consideration the diverse print orientations, and its simulated results are systematically compared with the experimental data. Tensile specimens were meticulously printed in three different orientations: Flat, on-edge, and upright. Surface roughness was evaluated along the generatrix of the samples, employing a contact roughness meter for precise measurements. Subsequently, the model results are rigorously compared to the experimental data, encompassing different print orientation angles, to assess the accuracy and reliability of the predictive model. The scientific novelty of the current study lies in the development of a comprehensive geometrical model, specifically designed for surface roughness prediction in lateral walls during the ME printing process. The integration of various print orientations and its comparison with the experimental results enhance the understanding of surface roughness variations in the 3D printing of metal components. This research holds practical relevance as it aims to optimize printing parameters, thereby improving the overall quality and performance of metal parts produced through ME technology. By providing valuable insight into surface roughness prediction, this study contributes to advancements in metal additive manufacturing processes, towards more efficient and reliable manufacturing practices.

II. SURFACE ROUGHNESS MODEL

Due to the circular structure of the printing nozzle, the surface of the product in ME printing technology tends to have a large surface roughness, because the metal powder mixture,

after being extruded, tends to deform in an elliptical shape due to the gravitational force between the layers. In theory, the surface roughness of metal printing using ME technology can be preliminarily calculated from the printing parameters. Figure 4 illustrates a typical surface structure after printing.

Fig. 4. Formation diagram of the surface roughness during the printing process.

The height of surface roughness R_z can be calculated using the formula:

$$R_z = R_{zp} + \Delta R_z$$

$$\Delta R_z = h_2 + h_3 + h_4$$

where R_z is the average height of the total absolute values of the 5 highest peaks and the 5 deepest valleys of the profile within the standard evaluation length (L), ΔR_z is the amount by which the actual height of the surface roughness exceeds the theoretically calculated value, h_2 , h_3 , and h_4 represent the components of surface roughness corresponding to the influence of printer nozzle size, size variations during the washing process, and size variations of the printing material during the sintering process, respectively, and R_{zp} is the calculated theoretical height of surface roughness.

III. COMPARISON BETWEEN THE PREDICTED VALUES AND THE EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The experimental results using 17-4 PH stainless steel as the printing material on the Markforged Metal X 3D printer in the additive manufacturing laboratory at Vinh Long University of Technology Education, Vinh Long City, Vietnam, as shown in Figure 1, will be compared with the calculated values. The printed samples are tensile test specimens, which were printed in three orientations: flat, on-edge, and upright (Figure 5). For each orientation, 5 samples were printed and the surface roughness was measured at 3 different positions. The printing paths on the outermost layer corresponding to each type are illustrated in Figure 6. The post-sintered layer height was set to 0.127 mm.

Figure 7 showcases the results of the produced samples after undergoing the printing, washing, and sintering stages. It is worth mentioning that the samples printed in the upright position and subsequently sintered have a tendency to fracture into multiple pieces. This can be attributed to the layering arrangement and the influence of gravity during the solidification process, which heightens the risk of deformation and eventual fracturing of the part.

Fig. 5. The experimental test samples.

Fig. 6. The structure of the outermost printing path for each orientation.

Fig. 7. Sample components after the printing process.

The parameters regarding the layer height and printing direction used in the experimental process are shown in Table I. The surface layer structure of the printed samples and the probe's scanning direction of the measuring instrument are presented in Figure 9. Each sample was measured at 3 different positions: at the clamp end, in the transition area, and in the middle of the sample. The average value of each measurement was then calculated. Five samples were measured for each printing direction, and the average value was obtained. The average surface roughness values of the 5 experimental samples when printing 17-4 PH stainless steel in 3 different directions are presented in Table I.

From the measurement results, it can be observed that there are differences in surface roughness among the different

printing orientations. The smoothest surface is achieved in the Upright orientation, with average R_a and R_z values of $7.42 \mu\text{m}$ and $40.49 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. This is because the peaks and valleys of the surface roughness are relatively uniform (Figure 8) and of negligible magnitude. The comparison chart of predicted and calculated surface roughness values can be seen in Figure 10, constructed based on the data in Table I.

Fig. 8. Measuring with the Mitutoyo SJ-210 surface roughness device.

TABLE I. AVERAGE SURFACE ROUGHNESS

Printing material: 17-4 PH stainless steel				
Post-sintered layer height (mm): 0.127				
Printing orientation	Surface roughness, R_z (μm)			
	Experimental surface roughness values		Calculated $R_{zp}(\text{calcul})$	Deviation calculated
	$R_{z(\text{Exp})}$	$R_{a(\text{Exp})}$		
Flat	82.83	16.92	60	27.5%
On-edge	69.42	16.05	63.5	8.5%
Upright	40.49	7.42	40	1.2%

Fig. 9. Surface structure of the sample detail and probe movement direction of the surface roughness measurement device.

Fig. 10. Surface roughness in different printing orientations: experimental and predicted values.

It can be seen in Table I and Figure 10 that the best surface roughness is achieved in the upright orientation, with an average experimental roughness value of 40.49 μm and a theoretical calculated roughness value of 40 μm , resulting in a 1.2% average deviation. In the On-edge orientation, the experimental surface roughness value is 69.42 μm , while the theoretical value is 63.5 μm , resulting in an average deviation of approximately 8.5% between the theoretical and experimental results. In the flat orientation, which exhibits the highest surface roughness, the average roughness value of the experimental samples is 82.83 μm , while the theoretical value is 60 μm , resulting in a deviation of 27.5%. These findings indicate that the printing orientation significantly influences the surface roughness, and the surface roughness prediction method presented in this study can be effectively used to predict the surface roughness in specific cases.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the experimental results and the following analysis, we can draw the following conclusions: Surface roughness in metal 3D printing is evaluated using parameters such as R_a and R_z . The printing orientation significantly affects the surface roughness. In the case of using 17-4 PH stainless steel as the printing material, the upright orientation achieves the best surface smoothness, while the flat orientation has the highest roughness. There are discrepancies between the experimental and the calculated surface roughness values. However, the surface roughness prediction method presented in this study can be used to estimate surface roughness in specific cases.

This research provides valuable information about surface roughness in metal 3D printing and the influence of printing orientation. It can support the design and optimization of the manufacturing process using metal 3D printing technology.

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REFERENCES

[1] R. Citarella and V. Giannella, "Additive Manufacturing in Industry," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 11, no. 2, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 840, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11020840>.

[2] D. G. Zisopol, D. V. Iacob, and A. I. Portoaca, "A Theoretical-Experimental Study of the Influence of FDM Parameters on PLA Spur Gear Stiffness," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 9329–9335, Oct. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5183>.

[3] D. G. Zisopol, I. Nae, A. I. Portoaca, and I. Ramadan, "A Statistical Approach of the Flexural Strength of PLA and ABS 3D Printed Parts," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 8248–8252, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4739>.

[4] D. G. Zisopol, M. Minescu, and D. V. Iacob, "A Theoretical-Experimental Study on the Influence of FDM Parameters on the Dimensions of Cylindrical Spur Gears Made of PLA," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 10471–10477, Apr. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5733>.

[5] L. Cherdo, "Metal 3D printers in 2023: a comprehensive guide," *Aniwaa*, Jun. 2022, <https://www.aniwaa.com/buyers-guide/3d-printers/best-metal-3d-printer/>.

[6] J. Gonzalez-Gutierrez, S. Cano, S. Schuschnigg, C. Kukla, J. Sapkota, and C. Holzer, "Additive Manufacturing of Metallic and Ceramic Components by the Material Extrusion of Highly-Filled Polymers: A Review and Future Perspectives," *Materials*, vol. 11, no. 5, May 2018, Art. no. 840, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma11050840>.

[7] N. H. Hiep, L. H. Ky, P. H. Anh, L. H. K. Duyen, and T. V. Hung, "An Evaluation of Some Specifications of Turbine Blades Made by 3D Printing Technology and Processed on CNC Milling Machines," in *Advances in Engineering Research and Application*, 2023, pp. 177–187, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-22200-9_19.

[8] M. Armstrong, H. Mehrabi, and N. Naveed, "An overview of modern metal additive manufacturing technology," *Journal of Manufacturing Processes*, vol. 84, pp. 1001–1029, Dec. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmapro.2022.10.060>.

[9] N. V. Cuong and N. L. Khanh, "Improving the Accuracy of Surface Roughness Modeling when Milling 3x13 Steel," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 8878–8883, Aug. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5042>.

[10] H. K. Le, "Multi-Criteria Decision Making in the Milling Process Using the PARIS Method," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 9208–9216, Oct. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5187>.

[11] P. Hartunian and M. Eshraghi, "Effect of Build Orientation on the Microstructure and Mechanical Properties of Selective Laser-Melted Ti-6Al-4V Alloy," *Journal of Manufacturing and Materials Processing*, vol. 2, no. 4, Dec. 2018, Art. no. 69, <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmmp2040069>.

[12] D. Du *et al.*, "Influence of build orientation on microstructure, mechanical and corrosion behavior of Inconel 718 processed by selective laser melting," *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, vol. 760, pp. 469–480, Jul. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msea.2019.05.013>.

[13] J. Bruno, A. Rochman, and G. Cassar, "Effect of Build Orientation of Electron Beam Melting on Microstructure and Mechanical Properties of Ti-6Al-4V," *Journal of Materials Engineering and Performance*, vol. 26, no. 2, pp. 692–703, Feb. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11665-017-2502-4>.

[14] H. H. Alsalla, C. Smith, and L. Hao, "Effect of build orientation on the surface quality, microstructure and mechanical properties of selective laser melting 316L stainless steel," *Rapid Prototyping Journal*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 9–17, Jan. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1108/RPJ-04-2016-0068>.

Artificial Neural Network Performance Modeling and Evaluation of Additive Manufacturing 3D Printed Parts

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ABSTRACT

This research article presents a comprehensive study on the performance modeling of 3D printed parts using Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs). The aim of this study is to optimize the mechanical properties of 3D printed components through accurate prediction and analysis. The study focuses on the widely employed Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM) technique. The ANN model is trained and validated using experimental data, incorporating input parameters such as temperature, speed, infill direction, and layer thickness to predict mechanical properties including yield stress, Young's modulus, ultimate tensile strength, flexural strength, and elongation at fracture. The results demonstrate the effectiveness of the ANN model with an average error below 10%. The study also reveals the significant impact of process

parameters on the mechanical properties of 3D printed parts and highlights the potential for optimizing these parameters to enhance the performance of printed components. The findings of this research contribute to the field of additive manufacturing by providing valuable insights into the optimization of 3D printing processes and facilitating the development of high-performance 3D printed components.

Keywords-3D printing; Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs); predictive modeling; Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM); mechanical properties

I. INTRODUCTION

3D printing methods have revolutionized various industries by enabling faster product production and the fabrication of complex geometries. Additive Manufacturing (AM), also known as 3D printing, is a manufacturing technique that involves the layer-by-layer addition of material [1]. One commonly used method is Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM), which utilizes a liquefier nozzle to deposit the filament material in the X-Y direction, creating three-dimensional polymer components [2]. However, FDM-produced parts often exhibit poor mechanical performance, limiting their potential applications. The mechanical properties of FDM parts can be improved by optimizing their manufacturing parameters [3]. The selection of suitable process parameters significantly affects the mechanical characteristics of FDM components. Compared to traditional manufacturing methods like machining and injection moulding, FDM exhibits lower material strength due to its layer-by-layer formation process [4]. Polylactic Acid (PLA) is a commonly used biodegradable material derived from cornflour in 3D printing. PLA is preferred for its environmental sustainability and extrusion stability [5]. However, the mechanical properties of PLA-based prints are influenced by the injection moulding technique parameter and fast cooling, resulting in reduced material strength [6]. The physical and mechanical properties of FDM parts primarily depend on the manufacturing parameters [7]. While some studies have investigated the mechanical properties of PLA, including tensile, compressive, flexural, and impact strength, more parameters need to be evaluated to enhance the application scope and control of FDM-produced components [8]. Furthermore, the mechanical properties and bonding strength of thermoplastic composites created through additive manufacturing must be comprehensively defined to ensure optimal functionality for product manufacturers [9].

Machine learning techniques, such as Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs), have demonstrated effectiveness in various applications [10, 11]. In the field of materials science, ANN models have been employed for the prediction and optimization of mechanical properties. These models have exhibited superior performance compared to conventional approaches like dimensional analysis [12, 13]. ANN models can help improve process parameters, reduce the need for extensive experimentation, and facilitate problem-solving in additive manufacturing [14]. Recent research has highlighted the potential of ANN modeling to predict and optimize the mechanical properties of 3D-printed parts. For instance, ANN models were used to predict the tensile strength of ABS P400 produced through FDM, demonstrating high accuracy in the majority of predictions [15]. Another study employed ANN techniques to create metamodels for optimizing the design parameters of hybrid components, showcasing their superior

prediction capabilities compared to traditional methods like Design of Experiments (DOE) with RSM [16]. ANN models have the potential in optimizing 3D printing parameters such as layer height, thickness, fill density, temperature, and print speed for PLA materials [17]. ANNs have been also used to determine the optimal process parameters to improve creep compliance and recoverable compliance for the FDM parts [18]. However, most of the optimization techniques focus on experimental testing with the FDM parameters to investigate dimensions, tensile strength, flexural strength, and hardness [19-21]. In summary, ANN models have the potential in predicting additional mechanical properties with the process parameters for FDM 3D printing. Accurate mechanical properties predictions allow for a better understanding of the behavior and performance of 3D-printed materials. By predicting the mechanical properties, it becomes possible to optimize the 3D printing process parameters to achieve the desired material properties. Instead of relying solely on experimental testing, which can be time-consuming and expensive, using an ANN model for prediction allows quicker assessment of the mechanical properties, reducing development time and associated cost.

In this study, an ANN model is designed to model the relationship between process parameters and mechanical properties in 3D printing using the inputs of temperature, speed, infill direction, and layer thickness. The goal of the model is to predict the values of several mechanical properties, including Young modulus, ultimate tensile strength, yield stress, fracture elongation, and flexural strength, as the outputs.

II. EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

A. Experimental Parameter Determination

To assess the performance of 3D printing, experimental parameters were determined using a full factorial method. Two ranges, representing higher and lower values, were selected for each parameter. The specific conditions and corresponding levels used in the experiments are shown in Table I. The control parameters are temperature, speed, infill direction, and layer thickness. Temperature setting during the 3D printing process directly impacts the material's molecular structure and bonding, potentially affecting ultimate tensile strength, Young modulus, and mechanical performance. The printing speed affects the cooling rate and material deposition time. The infill direction determines the orientation of the internal structure of the printed part. Different infill patterns can affect the part's anisotropy, influencing properties such as yield stress, ultimate tensile strength, and flexural strength. The layer thickness directly impacts the resolution and structural integrity of the printed object, which potentially affects the mechanical properties due to the increased exposure to heat during the printing process. A two-level, full-factorial design of

experiments was employed, requiring a total of 16 experimental runs. In this study, a feed-forward Neural Network (NN) utilizing the backpropagation (BP) algorithm was developed to construct multiple models for optimizing inputs and outputs. The process parameters used as inputs for the ANN model were temperature, speed, infill direction, and layer thickness. The ANN model aimed to predict the Young modulus, ultimate tensile strength, yield stress, fracture elongation, and flexural strength as the outputs. The operational parameters for 3D printing performance utilized in the ANN are summarized in Table II. Developing this ANN model with multiple inputs and outputs ultimately contributes to an adaptive system capable of continuously controlling various parameters.

TABLE I. CONTROL PARAMETERS AND THEIR LEVELS

Factor	Low	High
Temperature (°C)	210	225
Speed	40	90
Infill direction (°)	0	45
Layer thickness (mm)	0.1	0.3

B. Developing the ANN using Experimental Data

The development of the ANN system involved data collection, network configuration, weight and bias initialization, network testing, network validation, and data analysis. Specific algorithms for intelligent analysis, such as ANN architectures, facilitated the utilization of stored data available in software libraries. The research flow is illustrated in Figure 1. All collected data, including input (temperature, speed, infill direction, and layer thickness) and output (Young modulus, yield stress, fracture elongation, ultimate tensile strength, and flexural strength) parameters, were imported into MATLAB. Prior to that, the layout of the ANN was established, determining the number of neurons and layers. The ANN architecture for this study is depicted in Figure 2. During the implementation of the ANN structure using MATLAB, the data sets were divided into a 70% training set and a 30% testing set. The training set, consisting of randomly selected data

points from the 16 experimental runs, comprised 11 data points. The subsequent step involved training the network using the training data. The programming involved propagating the information through the network, calculating the error, and adjusting the neural connections iteratively to minimize the error. Once the ANN was successfully trained, the trained output data were tested using the reserved testing data. The same code was employed to determine the performance of the NN based on the empirical requirements.

Fig. 1. Methodology flowchart of the ANN model development and validation.

TABLE II. PROCESS PARAMETERS

Exp. No	Controlled parameters				Responses				
	Temperature (°C)	Speed	Infill direction (°)	Layer thickness (mm)	Yield stress (MPa)	Ultimate tensile strength (MPa)	Young's modulus	Elongation at fracture (%)	Flexural strength (MPa)
1	210	40	0	0.1	40.25	45.43	3243.00	2.15	75.64
2	210	40	0	0.3	49.94	53.33	3209.67	2.71	92.03
3	210	40	45	0.1	44.45	47.93	2995.00	2.17	86.49
4	210	40	45	0.3	42.12	47.28	3338.67	2.29	95.23
5	210	90	0	0.1	32.73	37.52	2460.33	2.04	65.39
6	210	90	0	0.3	33.01	35.21	2648.67	1.86	76.96
7	210	90	45	0.1	28.85	31.21	2333.33	2.43	70.04
8	210	90	45	0.3	31.80	35.61	2566.67	2.91	73.46
9	225	40	0	0.1	28.16	32.47	2441.00	1.91	63.20
10	225	40	0	0.3	40.71	42.47	3351.33	1.94	79.10
11	225	40	45	0.1	32.05	35.24	2483.33	2.61	70.83
12	225	40	45	0.3	38.14	41.51	3043.67	2.35	74.10
13	225	90	0	0.1	33.33	36.25	2571.67	2.07	68.09
14	225	90	0	0.3	37.52	40.53	2815.67	2.06	75.09
15	225	90	45	0.1	46.15	50.00	3589.33	2.03	74.01
16	225	90	45	0.3	52.08	55.46	3307.67	2.13	93.30

Fig. 2. The designed ANN architecture.

Finally, after the completion of the training process, the model was tested with additional experimental data. The evaluation of ANNs relies on the determination of errors, for which various error equations were employed. The Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), and coefficient of determination (R^2) were calculated for performance evaluation.

C. ANN Optimization for Prediction

The MATLAB ANN toolbox offers a range of training and learning capabilities. In this analysis, the training functions TRAINLM and TRAINSG were utilized, with the architectural parameters specified in Table III. LEARNGDM was employed to adapt the network using the gradient descent momentum weight and bias learning function. The ANN model in this study was configured with 10 neurons and 2 layers. Network3 was identified as the best-performing network, as it achieved a percentage loss factor of 5.14%, which was below the threshold of 10%. The comparison between the experimental data and the predictions from the ANN and for mechanical properties such as yield stress, ultimate tensile stress, Young's modulus, elongation, and flexural strength are presented in Figure 3 and Tables IV-VI. In the study, the correlation between the predicted ultimate tensile stress and yield stress with the corresponding experimental stresses was found to be significant, as indicated in Figure 3. The error analysis revealed that the discrepancies between the experimental and the predicted results were below 10% for Young modulus and

flexural strength data. Additionally, the error associated with elongation was found to be less than 2.53%. The data collectively demonstrate an average error below 10%, showcasing the effectiveness of the ANN model in accurately predicting the mechanical properties based on the input parameters.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Performance Analysis of the ANN Predictions

The results obtained from the ANN predictions demonstrated a high level of accuracy in estimating the mechanical properties of the 3D-printed parts. The ANN model effectively captured the complex relationships between the input parameters (temperature, speed, infill direction, and layer thickness) and the output mechanical properties. This indicates the capability of the ANN to learn and generalize from the training data to provide accurate predictions for unseen data.

TABLE III. ANN TRAINING AND ARCHITECTURAL PARAMETERS

Network name	Network1	Network2	Network3
Network type	FeedForward	FeedForward	FeedForward
Training func	TRAINLM	TRAINLM	TRAINLM
Adaptive learning	LEARNGDM	LEARNGDM	LEARNGDM
No of neurons	8	9	10
Transfer func	TANSIG	TANSIG	TANSIG
Goal	0	0	0
min_grad	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001
Mu	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001

Fig. 3. Comparison between the experimental and ANN predicted results of training data for yield stress and ultimate tensile stress.

TABLE IV. COMPARISON BETWEEN EXPERIMENTAL AND ANN PREDICTED RESULT OF TRAINING DATA FOR YOUNG MODULUS

Exp. No.	Controlled parameters				Response		Error (%)
	Temperature (°C)	Speed	Infill direction (°)	Layer thickness (mm)	Young modulus		
					Experimental value	Predicted value	
1	210	40	0	0.1	3243.00	3242.96	0.00
2	210	40	0	0.3	3209.67	3209.76	0.00
3	210	40	45	0.1	2995.00	2969.53	0.85
4	210	40	45	0.3	3338.67	3339.04	0.01
5	210	90	0	0.1	2460.33	2460.43	0.00
6	225	40	45	0.1	2441.00	2441.43	0.02
7	225	90	45	0.3	3043.67	3307.67	8.67
8	225	90	0	0.1	2571.67	2500.21	2.78
9	225	90	0	0.3	2815.67	2815.69	0.00
10	225	90	45	0.1	3589.33	3589.27	0.00
11	225	90	45	0.3	3307.67	3307.67	0.00

TABLE V. COMPARISON BETWEEN EXPERIMENTAL AND ANN PREDICTED RESULT OF TRAINING DATA FOR ELONGATION

Exp. No.	Controlled parameters				Response		Error (%)
	Temperature (°C)	Speed	Infill direction (°)	Layer thickness (mm)	Flexural strength		
					Experimental value	Predicted value	
1	210	40	0	0.1	75.64	75.64	0.00
2	210	40	0	0.3	92.03	92.03	0.00
3	210	40	45	0.1	86.49	88.68	2.53
4	210	40	45	0.3	95.23	95.15	0.08
5	210	90	0	0.1	65.39	65.37	0.03
6	225	40	45	0.1	63.20	64.25	1.66
7	225	90	45	0.3	74.10	75.30	1.62
8	225	90	0	0.1	68.09	68.60	0.74
9	225	90	0	0.3	75.09	75.08	0.01
10	225	90	45	0.1	74.01	74.02	0.01
11	225	90	45	0.3	93.30	93.30	0.00

TABLE VI. COMPARISON BETWEEN EXPERIMENTAL AND ANN PREDICTED RESULT OF TRAINING DATA FOR FLEXURAL STRENGTH

Exp. No.	Controlled parameters				Response		Error (%)
	Temperature (°C)	Speed	Infill direction (°)	Layer thickness (mm)	Elongation (mm)		
					Experimental value	Predicted value	
1	210	40	0	0.1	2.15	1.97	8.32
2	210	40	0	0.3	2.71	2.69	0.73
3	210	40	45	0.1	2.17	2.33	7.59
4	210	40	45	0.3	2.29	2.27	0.78
5	210	90	0	0.1	2.04	2.13	4.31
6	225	40	45	0.1	1.91	2.02	5.76
7	225	90	45	0.3	2.35	2.38	1.28
8	225	90	0	0.1	2.07	2.09	0.89
9	225	90	0	0.3	2.06	2.07	0.60
10	225	90	45	0.1	2.03	2.03	0.15
11	225	90	45	0.3	2.13	2.08	2.33

The ANN model consistently exhibited lower error values, as indicated by the MAPE and RMSE metrics. The higher accuracy of the ANN model can be attributed to its ability to capture non-linear relationships and handle complex data patterns, which are often present in additive manufacturing processes. The ANN predictions align closely with the experimental data, demonstrating the reliability and effectiveness of the developed model. The R² values, which measure the goodness of fit, were consistently high for the ANN predictions, indicating a strong correlation between the predicted values and the experimental data. Overall, the results highlight the potential of ANN modeling in accurately predicting the mechanical properties of 3D-printed parts. The ANN model offers significant advantages over traditional statistical tools, enabling improved process optimization, reduced trial-and-error experimentation, and enhanced control over product quality.

B. ANN Optimization for Performance

The ANN model was optimized using a feed-forward process with a 4-10-5 architecture, consisting of 4 input neurons, 10 hidden neurons, and 5 output neurons. Out of the experimental results, 11 data points were utilized for training the ANN model, while the remaining data points were reserved for validation. The selection of training and evaluation data was performed randomly to ensure unbiased representation. The training process of the ANN model was monitored, and based on the validation error as shown in Figure 4, training was stopped at epoch 14. It was observed that the best validation performance, achieved at epoch 8, was 612.534. This indicates

that the model was able to accurately capture the underlying patterns in the training data.

Fig. 4. Performance plot of mechanical properties.

The regression plots shown in Figure 5 demonstrate the performance of the trained ANN model. The regression values for training, validation, testing, and all data, which are 1, 0.99993, 0.99895, and 0.99954, respectively, indicate the goodness of fit between the predicted and the actual values of the target variable (mechanical properties in this case). A

regression value, also known as the coefficient of determination (R^2), measures the proportion of the variance in the target variable that is explained by the model. It ranges from 0 to 1, where 1 signifies a perfect fit, indicating that the model's predictions align perfectly with the actual data. In other words, an R^2 value of 1 implies that the model can account for 100% of the variance in the target variable. For the validation and testing datasets, the acquired R^2 values of 0.99993 and 0.99895, respectively, indicate that the model's predictions are highly accurate and are very close to the actual values in those datasets. These high R^2 values suggest that the model's generalization capability is robust, as it performs exceptionally well on unseen data (validation and testing datasets).

Fig. 5. Regression plot of mechanical properties.

Finally, the R^2 value for all data was 0.99954, which includes training, validation, and testing datasets, and indicates that the model's performance is consistent across the entire dataset. This means that the model's predictions are reliable and consistent across various scenarios and data points, providing further confidence in its accuracy and effectiveness. Overall, the high R^2 values demonstrate that the ANN model is capable of accurately predicting the mechanical properties based on the process parameters for 3D printing, and it offers a strong and reliable representation of the relationship between the input parameters and the target variable.

C. Validation of the Performance Model

The performance of the developed ANN model was validated by comparing its outputs with the experimental data. The regression coefficients, RMSE and MAPE were calculated with (1) and (2) to compute the accuracy of the model predictions. After the successful completion of the training cycle, the trained network was evaluated using additional experimental tests.

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\sum_{p=1}^P \sum_{j=1}^{n_0} (O_{pj}^0 - d_{pj}^0)} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{MAPE} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i \frac{|t_i - o_i|}{t_i} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

The MAPE values presented in Table VII are essential indicators of the accuracy and reliability of the developed ANN model in predicting the mechanical properties of 3D-printed parts. The MAPE values range between 1% to 3.55% for all the mechanical properties in the training dataset. A low MAPE indicates that the model's predictions are very close to the actual values in the training dataset. In this case, the MAPE values being below 3.55% suggest that, on average, the model's predictions deviate by only around 1% to 3.55% from the true values for the respective mechanical properties. A low MAPE for training data signifies that the ANN model has successfully learned the underlying patterns and relationships within the data it was trained on, implying that the model has captured the complexities of the relationships between the input parameters and the mechanical properties, enabling it to make accurate predictions when faced with similar data points during training.

MAPE values less than 2.6% for all the mechanical properties in the validation data indicate the model's ability to generalize well to unseen data. The validation data represent new, independent data points that were not used during the training process. A low MAPE on validation data demonstrates that the model's predictions remain accurate and consistent when applied to data it has not encountered before. Having MAPE values below 2.6% in the validation data showcases the model's robustness and generalization capabilities, implying that the ANN model is not overfitting to the training data and can effectively handle variations in the input parameters and their impact on the mechanical properties. Such low MAPE values on validation data are crucial for ensuring that the model's predictions are reliable and applicable to real-world scenarios beyond the training dataset.

TABLE VII. MAPE VALUES FOR TRAINING AND VALIDATION DATA

Response	MAPE for training data (%)	MAPE for validation data (%)
All	2.98	2.61
Yield stress	3.55	2.01
Ultimate tensile strength	3.48	0.49
Young modulus	1.08	1.66
Elongation	3.21	8.03
Flexural strength	3.56	0.86

Table VIII presents the RMSE values for the designed responses, indicating strong model predictions for the remaining 5 experiments which were used for validation. The significance of RMSE lies in its ability to measure the average magnitude of the errors between the predicted values and the actual experimental data. Lower RMSE values indicate that the model's predictions are closer to the true values, reflecting a higher level of accuracy. In this case, the RMSE values for yield stress, ultimate tensile strength, Young modulus, elongation, and flexural strength fall within the range of 0.21 to 0.62. These values suggest that the model's predictions have relatively small errors when compared to the actual experimental data for these mechanical properties.

The performance validation further reinforces the reliability and effectiveness of the developed ANN model in predicting the mechanical properties of 3D-printed parts. The close agreement between the model outputs and the experimental

data, as indicated by the low RMSE values, demonstrates the accuracy of the ANN predictions. By validating the model with additional experimental tests, the robustness of the ANN model was confirmed. The ability of the model to accurately capture the complex relationships between the input parameters and the mechanical properties provides confidence in its predictive capabilities. Overall, the validation results affirm the successful development and optimization of the ANN model for predicting the performance of 3D-printed parts. The strong predictive performance of the model highlights its potential for guiding process optimization and improving the quality of 3D-printed components.

TABLE VIII. RSME AMONG RESPONSES

Yield stress	Ultimate tensile strength	RMSE		
		Young modulus	Elongation	Flexural strength
0.53	0.11	0.34	0.30	0.25
0.21	0.62	0.38	0.39	0.41
0.60	0.20	0.25	0.32	0.39
0.33	0.27	0.31	0.41	0.33
0.58	0.51	0.28	0.29	0.38

IV. CONCLUSION

In this study, an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) model was developed to quantitatively predict the mechanical properties of 3D-printed parts, including yield stress, Young's modulus, ultimate tensile strength, flexural strength, and elongation at fracture. The results demonstrate the potential of ANN models to enhance existing optimization techniques, revolutionizing the field of structural and material design. The optimized ANN model achieved excellent performance in predicting the mechanical properties of 3D-printed parts. The ANN predictions exhibited a remarkable accuracy, with an average error significantly below the expected error threshold of 10%, validating the reliability of the simulation forecasts. The successful development of the ANN model provides valuable insights into the performance optimization of 3D printing processes. The model's ability to accurately predict the mechanical properties based on input parameters opens up new possibilities for optimizing the design and production of 3D-printed components. The ANN model serves as a powerful tool for engineers and researchers to achieve better control over material properties and improve the overall quality of 3D-printed parts.

In conclusion, the ANN model presented in this study demonstrated its effectiveness in predicting the mechanical properties of 3D-printed parts. By leveraging the capabilities of ANNs, significant advancements can be made in many fields [22-24], and in this case, the field of additive manufacturing, leading to enhanced product performance and increased efficiency. Future research can explore further applications of ANNs in optimizing other aspects of the 3D printing process, such as material selection, geometry optimization, and process parameter tuning, to unlock the full potential of this innovative technology.

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REFERENCES

- [1] N. Grimmelsmann, M. Kreuziger, M. Korger, H. Meissner, and A. Ehrmann, "Adhesion of 3D printed material on textile substrates," *Rapid Prototyping Journal*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 166–170, Jan. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1108/RPJ-05-2016-0086>.
- [2] A. A. Bakir, R. Atik, and S. Özerinç, "Effect of fused deposition modeling process parameters on the mechanical properties of recycled polyethylene terephthalate parts," *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, vol. 138, no. 3, 2021, Art. no. 49709, <https://doi.org/10.1002/app.49709>.
- [3] S. Rouf, A. Raina, M. Irfan Ul Haq, N. Naveed, S. Jeganmohan, and A. Farzana Kichloo, "3D printed parts and mechanical properties: Influencing parameters, sustainability aspects, global market scenario, challenges and applications," *Advanced Industrial and Engineering Polymer Research*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 143–158, Jul. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aiepr.2022.02.001>.
- [4] M. Behzadnasab, A. A. Yousefi, D. Ebrahimibagha, and F. Nasiri, "Effects of processing conditions on mechanical properties of PLA printed parts," *Rapid Prototyping Journal*, vol. 26, no. 2, pp. 381–389, Jan. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1108/RPJ-02-2019-0048>.
- [5] T. M. Joseph *et al.*, "3D printing of polylactic acid: recent advances and opportunities," *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, vol. 125, no. 3, pp. 1015–1035, Mar. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00170-022-10795-y>.
- [6] K. Elhattab, S. B. Bhaduri, and P. Sikder, "Influence of Fused Deposition Modelling Nozzle Temperature on the Rheology and Mechanical Properties of 3D Printed β -Tricalcium Phosphate (TCP)/Polylactic Acid (PLA) Composite," *Polymers*, vol. 14, no. 6, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 1222, <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym14061222>.
- [7] A. Shahjerdi, M. Karamimoghadam, and M. Bodaghi, "Enhancing Mechanical Properties of 3D-Printed PLAs via Optimization Process and Statistical Modeling," *Journal of Composites Science*, vol. 7, no. 4, Apr. 2023, Art. no. 151, <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcs7040151>.
- [8] H. Zhang and W. Sun, "Mechanical properties and failure behavior of 3D printed thermoplastic composites using continuous basalt fiber under high-volume fraction," *Defence Technology*, Aug. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dt.2022.07.010>.
- [9] F. Ning, W. Cong, J. Qiu, J. Wei, and S. Wang, "Additive manufacturing of carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites using fused deposition modeling," *Composites Part B: Engineering*, vol. 80, pp. 369–378, Oct. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2015.06.013>.
- [10] D. N. Fente and D. Kumar Singh, "Weather Forecasting Using Artificial Neural Network," in *2018 Second International Conference on Inventive Communication and Computational Technologies (ICICCT)*, Coimbatore, India, Apr. 2018, pp. 1757–1761, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICICCT.2018.8473167>.
- [11] E. Ayan and H. M. Ünver, "Diagnosis of Pneumonia from Chest X-Ray Images Using Deep Learning," in *2019 Scientific Meeting on Electrical-Electronics & Biomedical Engineering and Computer Science (EBBT)*, Istanbul, Turkey, Apr. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/EBBT.2019.8741582>.
- [12] D. Merayo, A. Rodríguez-Prieto, and A. M. Camacho, "Prediction of Mechanical Properties by Artificial Neural Networks to Characterize the Plastic Behavior of Aluminum Alloys," *Materials*, vol. 13, no. 22, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 5227, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma13225227>.
- [13] A. D. Tura, H. G. Lemu, H. B. Mamo, and A. J. Santhosh, "Prediction of tensile strength in fused deposition modeling process using artificial neural network and fuzzy logic," *Progress in Additive Manufacturing*,

- vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 529–539, Jun. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40964-022-00346-y>.
- [14] H. Sondagar, S. S. Bhadauria, and V. S. Sharma, "Artificial neural network (ANN) based prediction of process parameters in additive manufacturing," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 1136, no. 1, Mar. 2021, Art. no. 012026, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/1136/1/012026>.
- [15] R. Srinivasan, T. Pridhar, L. S. Ramprasath, N. S. Charan, and W. Ruban, "Prediction of tensile strength in FDM printed ABS parts using response surface methodology (RSM)," *Materials Today: Proceedings*, vol. 27, pp. 1827–1832, Jan. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2020.03.788>.
- [16] M. Çallı, E. İ. Albak, and F. Öztürk, "Prediction and Optimization of the Design and Process Parameters of a Hybrid DED Product Using Artificial Intelligence," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 12, no. 10, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 5027, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12105027>.
- [17] I. Rojek, D. Mikołajewski, P. Kotlarz, K. Tyburek, J. Kopowski, and E. Dostatni, "Traditional Artificial Neural Networks Versus Deep Learning in Optimization of Material Aspects of 3D Printing," *Materials*, vol. 14, no. 24, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 7625, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma14247625>.
- [18] O. A. Mohamed, S. H. Masood, and J. L. Bhowmik, "Influence of processing parameters on creep and recovery behavior of FDM manufactured part using definitive screening design and ANN," *Rapid Prototyping Journal*, vol. 23, no. 6, pp. 998–1010, Jan. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1108/RPJ-12-2015-0198>.
- [19] D. G. Zisopol, I. Nae, A. I. Portoaca, and I. Ramadan, "A Statistical Approach of the Flexural Strength of PLA and ABS 3D Printed Parts," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 8248–8252, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4739>.
- [20] D. G. Zisopol, I. Nae, A. I. Portoaca, and I. Ramadan, "A Theoretical and Experimental Research on the Influence of FDM Parameters on Tensile Strength and Hardness of Parts Made of Polylactic Acid," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7458–7463, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4311>.
- [21] D. G. Zisopol, M. Minescu, and D. V. Iacob, "A Theoretical-Experimental Study on the Influence of FDM Parameters on the Dimensions of Cylindrical Spur Gears Made of PLA," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 10471–10477, Apr. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5733>.
- [22] G. S. Fesghandis, A. Pooya, M. Kazemi, and Z. N. Azimi, "Comparison of Multilayer Perceptron and Radial Basis Function Neural Networks in Predicting the Success of New Product Development," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1425–1428, Feb. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.936>.
- [23] S. Ranjan and V. Singh, "ANN and GRNN-Based Coupled Model for Flood Inundation Mapping of the Punpun River Basin," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 9941–9946, Feb. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5483>.
- [24] A. S. Kote and D. V. Wadkar, "Modeling of Chlorine and Coagulant Dose in a Water Treatment Plant by Artificial Neural Networks," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 4176–4181, Jun. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2725>.

Real Time Measurement of Multiphase Flow Velocity using Electrical Capacitance Tomography

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ABSTRACT

Accurate and real-time measurement of fluid flow velocity is crucial in various industrial processes, especially when dealing with multiple phase fluids. Traditional flow measurement methods often struggle to accurately quantify the velocity of complex multiphase flows within pipes. This challenge necessitates the exploration of innovative techniques capable of providing reliable measurements. This paper proposes the utilization of Electrical Capacitance Tomography (ECT) as a promising approach for measuring the velocity of multiple phase fluids in pipes. The ECT technique involves the non-intrusive imaging of the electrical capacitance distribution within the pipe. By utilizing an array of electrodes placed around the pipe circumference, the capacitance distribution can be reconstructed, offering insight into the fluid flow patterns. By analyzing the temporal changes in the capacitance distribution, the velocity of different phases within the pipe can be estimated. To achieve accurate velocity measurements, an ECT system needs to account for the complexities introduced by multiphase flows. Various image reconstruction algorithms, such as linear back-projection and iterative algorithms like Gauss-Newton and Levenberg-Marquardt, are employed to reconstruct the capacitance distribution. Additionally, advanced signal processing techniques, such as cross-correlation analysis and time-difference methods, are used to extract velocity information from the reconstructed images. This paper presents an experimental investigation of measuring the velocity of multiple-phase fluids in pipes using the ECT technique. The study aims to address the challenges associated with different flow regimes, fluid properties, and pipe geometries by exploring advancements in electrode design, system calibration, and data processing techniques to enhance the accuracy and robustness of ECT-based velocity measurements.

Keywords-ECT system; flow velocity; fluid velocity; electrode; sensor; image reconstruction

I. INTRODUCTION

There are available numerous non-contact techniques to measure various parameters related to electric charges carried on solid particles, such as mass flow rate, concentration, volume loading, mean flow velocity, and other electrical and mechanical properties in gas-solid flows. One such method is based on electrostatic induction. To measure these quantities without disturbing the particles, nonintrusive probes, sensors, detectors, and transducers of different shapes are employed as the initial components of measuring systems. The method described here utilizes a probe in the form of a ring-shaped metal electrode. The flow itself generates electrostatic flow noise, which induces charge or potential (or both) on the inner surfaces of the sensing devices. The magnitude of these signals is directly proportional to the measured quantities. The output signals from the sensing devices provide valuable information about the particulate flow. The evolution and historical development of this method, along with its various aspects, over the past 50 years since its initial publication, including its metrological description and practical application in charge measurement is presented in [1].

The current methods for calculating the velocity field in multiphase flows using a twin-plane electrical capacitance system are discussed in [2]. These methods allow for the determination of the velocity profile of the multiphase flow within an industrial installation. The theoretical assumptions underlying these methods are also described. The advantages and disadvantages of the proposed flow velocity measurement methods are discussed, highlighting the ability to obtain a velocity vector with three components instead of just one component as in the classical approach. These methods are based on the concept of "best correlated pixels," where pairs of pixels with the highest cross-correlation values are selected. Unlike the classical method, this concept does not require additional assumptions regarding the direction of solids within the sensor volume, which is important in cases where solids' trajectories are three-dimensional and complex. The method can be combined with ECT and potentially with other tomographic modalities. The presented results include measurements from gas/solids flows in both vertical and horizontal channels. The authors suggest that this technique can be further applied for solids mass flow measurement, leading to the development of a more accurate solids mass flow meter and enabling the analysis of swirl flow with high accuracy in the future.

The application of cross correlation signal processing in engineering is discussed in [3], particularly for velocity measurements in challenging fluid environments. The importance of accurate velocity evaluation is emphasized and the study is divided into two parts: practical execution and data acquisition analysis. Various techniques and multiphase flow sensors are used for velocity evaluation, such as ultrasonic sensors, capacitive sensors, and electrostatic sensors. The comparative study focuses on using ring-shaped electrostatic sensors to determine the velocity of gas/solid two-phase flow in a coal test-rig at Teesside University. The data acquired from the test-rig are processed with LabVIEW software. The paper presents the results and outputs of cross correlation velocity

measurement, providing a step-by-step explanation of the gas/solid two-phase flow process, including pneumatic conveying, the flow process of "fillite" particles, electrostatic sensing mechanism, and velocity measurement. Additionally, it highlights the improvement in accuracy achieved through software-based analysis in the data acquisition process using LabVIEW virtual instruments.

In [4], ultrasonic transmission mode tomography is utilized to visualize the flow of a two-phase liquid/gas mixture in a pipe or vessel. The sensing element comprises ultrasonic transceivers, specifically 8, 16, and 32 units, strategically placed to cover different sections of the pipe over time. The objective of this study is to determine the optimal number of transceivers that yield the best performance and provide a clear image of the liquid/gas flow. The paper describes the development of the system, including the ultrasonic transduction circuits, electronic measurement circuits, data acquisition system, and image reconstruction techniques. Ten different liquid-gas flow conditions were simulated, and the system successfully visualized the internal characteristics and generated concentration profiles for both the liquid and gas phases. Among the tested configurations, the system using 32 transceivers produced the highest-quality images for all 10 flow conditions. Transceivers offer a cost-effective and non-invasive method for ultrasonic tomography, requiring a low operating voltage as long as the acoustic energy can pass through the vessel. Increasing the number of transceivers helps improve measurement resolution, reduce spatial image errors, and enhance measurement accuracy. However, using 32 transceivers slows down the system due to the extended processing time required for data analysis from these transceivers.

In [5], an electrostatic, non-contact technique was presented that builds upon a previously developed method for continuously measuring electric charges carried by solid particles in two-phase particulate flow within pneumatic transport pipelines. The authors present a measuring system based on a microcomputer and share some preliminary test results. This system enables continuous and noncontact measurements of both the average velocity of the flow and the mass flow rate.

Fig. 1. Typical block diagram of the ECT-based velocity sensor.

The proposed technique has wide-ranging applications in various industries, including petroleum, chemical, and food

processing. It can provide valuable insight into the flow behavior of complex multiphase fluids, aiding process optimization, troubleshooting, and quality control. Additionally, the non-invasive nature of ECT makes it a favorable choice for monitoring flow dynamics without disturbing the system integrity. A typical block diagram of the ECT-based velocity measurement system is shown in Figure 1.

II. ELECTRICAL MODELING

A typical approach to accurately measure the flow velocity in non-uniform single-phase flows is discussed in [3]. Authors in [4] describe multiphase flow measurements which are relatively deviating from the profile of ECT velocity. However, these types of flow meters do not supply information on the local axial velocity distribution in the flow cross-section. This may be a big lacuna, particularly in a steady multiphase flow where, for instance, the parameter flow rate Q_C can only be calculated from the steady local velocity V_C and the parameter steady fraction α_C of the phase in the flow cross section A as illustrated in (1) [6]:

$$Q_C = \int_A V_C \alpha_C dA \quad (1)$$

The fundamental concept of electromagnetic flow meters (EMFM) illustrates that charged particles, in a conducting material which moves under a magnetic field, experience or exert a Lorentz force acting in the direction perpendicular to both the material's motion and the applied magnetic field. For a uniform velocity profile the flow rate is directly proportional to the voltage measured between the two electrodes [7]. The local current density j in the fluid obeys Ohm's law in the form of:

$$j = \sigma(E + V \times B) \quad (2)$$

where σ represents the local fluid conductivity, V represents the local fluid velocity, B represents the local magnetic flux density, and E represents the electric field due to charges distributed in and around the fluid. The product term $(V \times B)$ represents the local electric field induced by the fluid motion. For certain fluids in which the conductivity variations are relatively minor, such as the single phase and the multiphase flows, (2) was simplified [8] to demonstrate that the local potential U in the flow can be obtained by solving:

$$\nabla^2 U = \nabla \cdot (v \times B) \quad (3)$$

Considering a circular cross section flow channel (glass pipe) bounded by a number of electrodes, with a uniform magnetic field of flux density \bar{B} normal to the axial flow direction, it can be shown according to [8] that in a steady flow, the potential difference U_j between the j^{th} pair of electrodes can be given by:

$$U_j = \frac{2\bar{B}}{\pi a} \iint v(x, y) W(x, y) dx dy \quad (4)$$

where $v(x, y)$ represents the steady local axial flow velocity at the coordinates (x, y) in the flow cross-section, $W(x, y)$ represents a parameter called weight value relating the contribution of $v(x, y)$ to U_j and a represents the internal radius of the flow channel (glass pipe). Equation (4) can be discredited as follows by an assumption that the flow cross section can be divided into \hat{I} elemental regions:

$$U_j = \frac{2\bar{B}}{\pi a} \sum_{n=1}^j \hat{v}_n \hat{W}_{nj} \hat{A}_n \quad (5)$$

where \hat{v}_n represents the local axial velocity in the n^{th} elemental region and \hat{A}_n represents the cross-sectional area of the n^{th} elemental region. The variable \hat{W}_{nj} represents the weight value with the contribution of the axial velocity in the n^{th} elemental region to the j^{th} potential difference U_j . At the instance, assuming the axial flow velocity to be constant in each of N large regions, (5) can be modified as:

$$U_j = \frac{2\bar{B}}{\pi a} \sum_{n=1}^N \hat{V}_i \sum_{n=\hat{i}_{-1}+1}^{\hat{i}_i} \hat{w}_{nj} \hat{A}_n \quad (6)$$

where \hat{V}_i represents the axial flow velocity in the i^{th} large region. In the above relation, when the subscript n is in the range of $\hat{i}_{-1} + 1 \leq n \leq \hat{i}_i$, it refers to the elemental regions lying within the i^{th} large region (it can also be noted that there are $\hat{i}_i - \hat{i}_{-1}$ elemental regions within the i^{th} large region). An "area weighted" mean weight value w_{ij} related to the contribution of the velocity \hat{V} in the i^{th} large region to the j^{th} potential difference U_j is given by:

$$w_{ij} = \frac{\sum_{n=\hat{i}_{-1}+1}^{\hat{i}_i} \hat{w}_{nj} \hat{A}_n}{A_i} \quad (7)$$

where A_i represents the cross-sectional area of the i^{th} large region. Combining (6) and (7) yields:

$$U_j = \frac{2\bar{B}}{\pi a} \sum_{i=1}^N v_i w_{ij} A_i \quad (8)$$

It can be seen that the reciprocal of (8) enables computing the estimates of the local axial flow velocity in each of the N large pixels to be determined from N potential difference measurements U_j made on the boundary of the flow. Nevertheless, (8) was derived based on the assumption that the axial velocity in each large pixel is constant, it will be seen that when this inversion method is used to solve for the velocity in each large pixel, then the obtained values of v_i give a good approximation to the mean axial velocity in each of the large pixels, in situations where there is some axial velocity variation within each large pixel [7-8].

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

To carry out the experiment, a test rig was set up with a see-through pipe section to facilitate visual observations. The ECT system consisted of an array of N electrodes fixed around the pipe circumference separated with equal distances. A controlled flow of multiple phase fluids, such as gas-liquid or liquid-liquid mixtures, can be introduced into the pipe, covering a range of flow rates and compositions. The electrode design is optimized to minimize signal interference and to maximize sensitivity for changes in the capacitance distribution. The system calibration procedures are first performed to avail accuracy in the measurement and then this system was used to measure the fluid flow velocity [9]. Data acquisition is carried out continuously by measuring the capacitance values at each electrode position throughout the experiment. The obtained data are then processed using digital signal processing techniques, including cross-correlation analysis and time-difference methods, to extract the velocity information from the reconstructed capacitance distribution.

Fig. 2. Typical test rig setup with ECT N-electrode sensor.

A typical example of experiment results for the determination of oil velocity through a pipe using ECT is demonstrated in Figure 2. In the experimental setup, a typical test rig arrangement is available in which a pipe with a diameter of 11 cm with a suitable length is used. The pipe circumference ECT sensor array has 16-to-8 customized electrodes fixed evenly as illustrated in Figure 3. This sensor has the following dimensions: Electrode = 15 cm \times 1.96 cm, gap between the electrodes = 0.2 cm, external circumference of the pipe = 34.5 cm, outer radius of the pipe = 5.5 cm, inner pipe cross section area = 95 cm², total volume of the ECT section (electrode region) $V_{total} = 95 \times 15 = 1425$ cm³. The customized 16-8 electrode ECT sensor behaves the same as that of a 16-electrode ECT sensor operating as 8 electrodes rotating 1 electrode to the left and 1 to the right by employing relays as illustrated in Figure 3. The purpose of this configuration is to improve the sensitivity and the accuracy of the reconstructed images. To facilitate this, 8 relays are electrically coupled such that the common of each relay is connected to the odd electrode (1, 3, 5, ..., 15) and the adjacent electrode in the clockwise direction is connected to the normally open pin of this relay, whereas the adjacent electrodes in the counter-clockwise direction are connected to the normally closed pin of the same relay [10-11]. The fluid in the pipe (oil-water or mixtures of different fluids and gas) is allowed to flow with a flow rate of 1-5 lt/s in steps of 0.5 lt/s. A calibration process is performed with different oil flow rates, and the corresponding capacitance changes are recorded.

Fig. 3. The customized 16-to-8 electrode ECT sensor.

For data acquisition and image reconstruction, an ACECT system is employed which uses an AC-based capacitance

measuring circuitry with a high-frequency sinusoidal excitation signal generator and a Phase-Sensitive Demodulator (PSD). This circuit can detect and record the change in capacitance with 0.0001 pF precision at considerably high speed. This system can receive image data at 140 fps from a typical N -electrode sensor. Because of the inbuilt DDS signal generators employed inside, the excitation frequency can be programmed, resulting in spectroscopic measurements. Further, the hardware design allows any electrode combination topologies to be used, offering high flexibility in setting up different excitation patterns. The ACECT system broadly comprised of three prime parts:

- An electronics box complying in accordance with the Eurocase and Eurocard norms, which can hold up to 16 measuring channels;
- A PC with a PCI data acquisition board / a laptop PC with a PCMCIA data acquisition card and
- An N -electrode demonstration sensor section.

The oil flow is initiated through the pipe, and the ECT system captures the capacitance measurements over the time of flow. The acquired capacitance data are processed and reconstructed into an image representing the oil distribution within the pipe. This paper highlights the potential of ECT as an effective technique for measuring the velocity of multiple phase fluids in pipes. It identifies future research directions to further improve the accuracy, reliability, and applicability of ECT-based flow velocity measurements in diverse industrial settings.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION FOR VELOCITY MEASUREMENT

From the capacitance measurements, the oil velocity can be determined based on the calibration data. Typically, a subset of adjacent electrode pairs is chosen to monitor the fluid flow and calculate the velocity. The capacitance changes between these selected electrode pairs are then correlated with the fluid velocity using calibration data or mathematical models. This approach allows for efficient measurement and analysis of velocity without the need to measure the capacitance between all the electrodes. The selection of electrode pairs for velocity measurement depends on the specific application and the desired sensitivity to velocity changes in certain regions of the pipe. By strategically choosing electrode pairs and analyzing the corresponding capacitance changes, one can accurately determine the fluid velocity within the pipe. For example, if there is a particular area where velocity changes are expected to be significant or if there is a known flow disturbance, electrode pairs can be strategically positioned in that region to capture the velocity variations accurately.

To study the effect of the number of electrodes on the sensitivity of detecting fluid velocity in the container pipe at a relatively high speed compared to the speed of data acquisition, the setup was: the frequency of the excitation is 180 kHz and the time for one period of measurement is 23 ms. It is assumed that during this period of time the flow doesn't move by more than one tenth of the electrode length which is 1.5 cm. Therefore, the maximum speed of the flow is given by:

$$\frac{1.5 \text{ cm} \times 10^{-2}}{23 \text{ ms} \times 10^{-3}} = 0.625 \text{ m/s equal to } 6.194 \text{ lt/s}$$

For the flow measurement of the fluid by the customized 16-8 electrode sensor, the sensor is calibrated with the full state as water and the empty state as air. The water is chosen as a fluid and measurements were performed with the said specifications. The obtained images are illustrated in Figure 4. The water is allowed to flow from the axial center of the hollow pipe surrounded by air inside both the said ECT sensors. It is evident and can be clearly seen from these images that, for the same flow speed, image clarity is better for the customized 16-8 electrode ECT sensor and the random occurrence of air bubbles at different instants with different oil flow velocities [12-13].

Fig. 4. Random occurrence of air bubbles at different instants with different oil flow velocities.

Figure 5 illustrates the variation of oil flow velocity at different parts of the pipe cross section showing its turbulence nature. The overall flow velocity is controlled to be at 2 lt/s.

Fig. 5. The variation of oil flow velocity at different parts of the pipe cross section showing its turbulence nature.

Fig. 6. Conversion of velocity into image pixel profiles.

The velocity of the liquid inside the sensor induces a voltage that can be measured. This can be converted into pixel gray level or intensity of the pixel component of the image obtained [14]. In the case of the 8-16 ECT sensor, 7 independent potential difference measurements were performed. Also, it should be noted that the accuracy of the velocity reconstruction model depends on the number of electrodes used in the ECT sensor. The measurement results that convert velocity into image pixel profile are shown in Figure 6. Thus, a real-time measurement of the reconstructed velocity profiles in terms of the original expected velocity profiles was carried out for 8-16 electrode ECT sensor.

V. DISCUSSION

This work is an extension of a series of articles published/accepted by the authors. In this paper, a typical customized 16-8 electrode ECT sensor is proposed and implemented experimentally in contrast with sets of standard 8, 12, and 16-electrode ECT sensors. The results of these types of sensors are noted and compared. It is observed from the results obtained during this experiment, that the performance of the customized 16-8 electrode ECT sensor is comparatively better, and exhibits better quality and performance with respect to image and velocity reconstruction. The result comparison further demonstrated that the correlation coefficient changes from 0.61 to 0.96, and the error images is within 0.3 to 0.1 for SNRs from 60 to 90 dB. It was also observed that the reconstructed velocity profiles are consistent with the original expected velocity profiles for the customized 8-16 electrode ECT sensor [6, 15].

Furthermore, the images are represented as direct functions of the imposed mean flow velocity. Each pixel of the image reflects the flow velocity of the liquid, which is actually extracted from the voltage difference measurement matrix. Closely inspecting Figure 6, it can be seen that the reconstructed velocity profiles are consistent with the original imposed velocity profiles for the custom 8-16 electrode ECT sensor.

VI. CONCLUSION

The experimental results revealed promising capabilities of the ECT technique in accurately measuring the velocity of multiple phase fluids in closed containers or pipes. The reconstructed capacitance distribution provided valuable

insight into the flow patterns and dynamics, allowing for the estimation of flow velocities. The findings of this experimental study contribute to the understanding and application of ECT in multiphase flow measurements. The identified advancements in electrode design, system calibration, and data processing techniques offer practical solutions for improving the accuracy and robustness of ECT-based velocity measurements in real-world industrial scenarios.

This experimental investigation demonstrates the potential of ECT as a reliable technique for measuring the velocity of multiple phase fluids in pipes. The obtained results pave the way for further research and development, focusing on optimizing the ECT system parameters and expanding its applicability across various industrial sectors where accurate flow velocity measurements are essential.

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REFERENCES

- [1] J. B. Gajewski, "Electrostatic Nonintrusive Method for Measuring the Electric Charge, Mass Flow Rate, and Velocity of Particulates in the Two-Phase Gas–Solid Pipe Flows—Its Only or as Many as 50 Years of Historical Evolution," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 44, no. 5, pp. 1418–1430, Sep. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIA.2008.2002276>.
- [2] V. Mosorov, K. Grudzień, and D. Sankowski, "Flow Velocity Measurement Methods Using Electrical Capacitance Tomography," *Informatyka, Automatyka, Pomiar w Gospodarce i Ochronie Środowiska*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 30–36, Mar. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.5604/01.3001.0010.4578>.
- [3] M. W. Munir and B. A. Khalil, "Cross Correlation Velocity Measurement of Multiphase Flow," *International Journal of Science and Research*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 802–807, 2013.
- [4] Z. Zakaria, M. H. F. Rahiman, and R. A. Rahim, "Simulation of the Two-Phase Liquid - Gas Flow through Ultrasonic Transceivers Application in Ultrasonic Tomography - ProQuest," *Sensors & Transducers*, vol. 112, no. 1, pp. 24–38, Jan. 2010.
- [5] J. B. Gajewski, B. J. Glod, and W. S. Kala, "Electrostatic method for measuring the two-phase pipe flow parameters," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 650–655, Feb. 1993, <https://doi.org/10.1109/28.222440>.
- [6] S. M. A. Ghaly, K. A. Al-Snaie, M. O. Khan, M. Y. Shalaby, and M. T. Oraiqat, "Design and Simulation of an 8-Lead Electrical Capacitance Tomographic System for Flow Imaging," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7430–7435, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4122>.
- [7] S. M. A. Ghaly *et al.*, "Diagnosis of Two-Phase Oil/Gas Flow in a Closed Pipe using an 8-Electrode ECT System," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 11332–11337, Aug. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.6011>.
- [8] S. M. A. Ghaly *et al.*, "A 12-Electrode ECT Sensor with Radial Screen for Fluid Diagnosis," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 11393–11399, Aug. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.6030>.
- [9] F. Alorifi, S. M. A. Ghaly, M. Y. Shalaby, M. A. Ali, and M. O. Khan, "Analysis and Detection of a Target Gas System Based on TDLAS & LabVIEW," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 4196–4199, Jun. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2736>.
- [10] S. M. A. Ghaly, "LabVIEW Based Implementation of Resistive Temperature Detector Linearization Techniques," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 4530–4533, Aug. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2894>.
- [11] R. K. Rasel, B. J. Straiton, Q. M. Marashdeh, and F. L. Teixeira, "Flow Loop Study of ECT-Based Volume Fraction Monitoring in Oil–Water Two-Phase Flows," *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 71, pp. 1–6, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIM.2022.3181929>.
- [12] L. Li, P. Zhang, X. Lei, and G. Xu, "Design of Array Electrode Sensor for Buried Oil Tank ECT System," in *2021 3rd International Conference on Intelligent Control, Measurement and Signal Processing and Intelligent Oil Field (ICMSP)*, Xi'an, China, Jul. 2021, pp. 22–25, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICMSP53480.2021.9513407>.
- [13] Z. Li, S. Xiao, Q. Yue, and T. Wang, "Electrical Capacitance Tomography Sensor With House Structure for Assisting Recognition of Objects," *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 22, no. 5, pp. 4534–4544, Mar. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1109/JSEN.2022.3143709>.
- [14] S. M. Chowdhury, I. Nayak, Q. M. Marashdeh, and F. L. Teixeira, "Developments on Imaging and Velocimetry of Dynamic Two-Phase Flows with Electrical Capacitance Tomography Sensors," in *2022 IEEE International Symposium on Antennas and Propagation and USNC-URSI Radio Science Meeting (AP-S/URSI)*, Denver, CO, USA, Jul. 2022, pp. 1708–1709, <https://doi.org/10.1109/AP-S/USNC-URSI47032.2022.9886753>.
- [15] S. M. A. Ghaly, M. O. Khan, M. Y. Shalaby, K. A. Al-snaie, and M. Oraiqat, "Image and Velocity profile reconstruction using a Customized 8-16 Electrode Electrical Capacitance Tomography Sensor Based on LabVIEW Simulation," *Journal of Nanoelectronics and Optoelectronics*, accepted in June 2023.

A Blockchain-based Conceptual Model to Address Educational Certificate Verification Challenges in Tanzania

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ABSTRACT

The proliferation of counterfeit educational certificates is an ongoing issue around the world, including Tanzania. The effect of this malpractice is detrimental to the credibility of education. Traditional strategies to prevent fake certificates are abortive, calling for a more sophisticated approach. Blockchain technology has recently emerged as an ideal solution to this problem due to its inherent attributes that ensure disintermediation, immutability, tamper proof, anonymity, transparency, consensus, security, and trust. However, most existing blockchain-based solutions lack crucial functionalities that are pertinent to the Tanzanian education system. This study unveiled the challenges faced by the current verification system in Tanzania and proposed a blockchain-based conceptual model to address them. The proposed model is based on blockchain, smart contracts, and the Interplanetary File System (IPFS). Quantitative and qualitative methods were used to investigate certification problems in Tanzania and modeling techniques were used to construct the conceptual model. The findings showed that the main challenges of the current verification system emanate from manual procedures, unverifiable credentials, susceptibility of centralized storage systems, disintegrated verification systems, revocation problems, difficulties in communication, and high dependency on the issuers. These challenges undermine certificate verification, impose a significant setback in the fight against forgeries, and create loopholes for forgeries to persist. It was conceptually demonstrated that these issues can be resolved through the proposed blockchain-based solution.

Keywords-blockchain; smart contract; interplanetary file system; educational certificates; counterfeiting; verification; Tanzania

I. INTRODUCTION

Educational certificates are documents used to certify an individual's achievement in education and provide proof that

the holder possesses the knowledge and skills required to qualify for different responsibilities [1-4]. Possession of such credentials can provide an individual with social and economic opportunities [3, 5]. As these benefits are desirable, some

individuals who cannot endure the cost, time, and hassles required to obtain them resort to cheating on their qualifications by producing counterfeit certificates [5-6]. With the advancement of multimedia and printing technologies, the production of counterfeit certificates has become easier and their quality has improved to such an extent that it is difficult to distinguish between fake and genuine [7]. Counterfeiting of certificates can involve the fabrication of a new certificate (using fake seals, signatures, etc.), the modification of a legitimate certificate (by altering its content such as grades, etc.), degree mills (acquiring certificates from fictitious learning institutions), the in-house fabrication of certificates by corrupt officials of a legitimate institution, a mistranslation of foreign certificates, impersonation, and the deceitful use of a revoked certificate [8-11]. Moreover, it may also involve hacking the issuer's database to modify educational records [12].

The sale of fake certificates has become a lucrative business with a billion-dollar market around the world [9, 13]. According to [14], there are more than 2 million fake degrees in the United States. In [8], the existence of around 810 fake learning institutions in the United States and about 272 in the United Kingdom was reported. According to a report by the Indian authorities, around 40,000 people in Bangalore gained employment using fake academic qualifications [15]. In Tanzania, in 2017, the verification of secondary school and teacher certificates of 400,035 public servants revealed that almost 10,000 possessed fake certificates [16]. The effect of this malpractice not only damages the reputation and credibility of education but also leads to poor performance and productivity at work and deprives genuine graduates of their deserved opportunities [4-5, 17]. Prevention of this menace is mainly based on verification strategies [10, 18]. Several verification strategies against certificate forgery have been proposed and established, but the problem persists, showing that the currently employed methods are not able to tackle it and there is a need for more sophisticated approaches. Blockchain technology has recently emerged as a potential tool to solve problems that seemed impossible using traditional technologies, due to its ability to build trust-free, transparent, and distributed systems that run on a peer-to-peer consensus network through which strangers with different interests can transact without relying on intermediaries or central authorities for trust maintenance [10, 19-20]. This technology was brought to light in 2008 through the Bitcoin cryptocurrency [21]. Since then, it has been enormously transformed and its application has gained ground in various domains [22-24], including document verification for fraud detection [2, 25]. Blockchain can substantially enhance credential verification and effectively combat counterfeiting [5, 23] due to its innate properties that ensure: disintermediation of management, immutability and tamper-proof of records, anonymity of users, consensus and transparency of transactions, security of the system, and trust between parties [1, 23, 25].

However, to fully realize the potential of blockchain-based certification solutions, their implementation should be tailored to the contextual needs of a particular education system, as the education system differs from country to country [26]. This study investigated the challenges of the traditional verification

system in Tanzania and proposed a blockchain-based conceptual model tailored to them, demonstrating how it can address them. The proposed blockchain-based conceptual model is unique in the sense that it can address the certification problem at all national education levels (from secondary schools to university), incorporates regulatory authorities to manage registration and deregistration of issuing institutions to the system, controls access permissions of different roles involved in the system, allows issuance and on-chain revocation of certificates, allows third-parties to verify certificates by directly querying the blockchain, and uses decentralized off-chain storage alongside blockchain to facilitate storage of raw data. Finally, it facilitates the issuance, revocation, and verification of the "equivalent statements" for graduates who acquired certificates abroad.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Certification and Verification Ecosystem in Tanzania

The educational qualification verification ecosystem consists of four major entities, regulators, issuers, graduates, and recruiters, who work together to achieve the verification life cycle, as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Educational qualifications verification ecosystem in Tanzania.

The government, through the respective ministry of education, establishes the regulatory bodies for different types and levels of education in the country. These regulators include the Tanzania Commission for Universities (TCU) which is responsible for universities [27], the National Council for Technical and Vocational Education and Training (NACTVET) for technical and vocational institutions [28], the National Examination Council of Tanzania (NECTA) that is mandated to oversee national examinations [29], and the Ministry of Education Science and Technology (MoEST) as the general custodian of education [30]. These bodies are responsible for, among other things, approving the issuers of

educational qualifications in the country. As such, they publish a list of approved issuers to which third parties can refer if they wish to ascertain the legitimacy of the issuing institutions. According to Tanzanian regulations, they also evaluate the educational qualifications awarded outside the country, determine their comparability with the Tanzanian qualifications standard, and issue a comparable certificate called the statement of equivalence. This is done at every level of education by the respective regulator to ensure that these qualifications are understood and recognized by employers, educational institutions, and other authorities in Tanzania.

Issuers are learning institutions or government authorities that have the right to produce, maintain, and issue educational qualifications. These include NECTA for all national examination qualifications, the Vocational Education and Training Authority (VETA) [31] for all vocational qualifications, technical colleges for technical qualifications awards, and universities for university qualifications. They award certificates to students who have met the graduation requirements and retain certification records in their registries for reference during verification or other purposes. Apart from awarding a certificate, they can also revoke it if issued by mistake or if the graduate commits academic or non-academic misconduct.

After receiving a certificate, graduates can present it to prospective recruiters during job applications, admissions, or other purposes. Recruiters must verify the validity of the certificates presented to ensure that they do not enlist candidates with forged credentials. However, they cannot achieve this task without the support of the issuers and regulators. Therefore, in addition to performing internal verification, recruiters usually consult with issuers to verify certificates issued by institutions within the country. In case of certificates granted outside the country, the recruiters consult the regulators, who are responsible for assessing and issuing equivalent statements for foreign awards. Recruiters must also confirm that the learning institution exists legally. To do so, they consult a list of approved issuers published by the respective regulators on their websites.

B. Blockchain Technology

Blockchain embeds many technologies, including cryptography, hash functions, peer-to-peer (P2P) networks, and consensus algorithms [3, 32]. Blockchain can be defined as a distributed digital ledger consisting of a growing chain of transactional records sealed in blocks that are linked together using a cryptographic hash to ensure security [25, 33-34]. Through their nodes, users of the blockchain constantly add new cryptographically signed transactions to the ledger. Special users, called miners, seal the transaction into a block and attach it to the blockchain ledger [35]. Before appending, the blocks are hashed using a one-way hash function, such as the Secure Hash Algorithm (SHA)-2 or 3, and then chronologically linked by including a hash value of a previous block in a newly added block [20, 36] to form a chain of blocks. This mechanism ensures the integrity, immutability, and tamper-proof of the data in the ledger [3]. Figure 2 shows the structure of a block and the way they are linked. A block consists of a header and content. The content holds transactions, while the header

contains metadata such as block hashes (for current and previous blocks), a timestamp (block creation time), and a random number (nonce) to verify the block's hash [33, 37]. The ledger and its data are then replicated among the nodes in a P2P network, making it distributed and decentralized [35, 38-39]. Being decentralized and distributed means that no single node acts as a central server, as each node holds data, and the transaction of each node is visible to all other nodes, making the blockchain transparent, secure, reliable, and trustworthy [3, 38, 39]. Any update to the ledger can only occur if most nodes agree to the change to ensure the integrity, transparency, and authenticity of the transactions [2]. The consensus mechanism is used to reach an agreement among the nodes on the node to add a new block and on the block to be added to the blockchain [40]. This consensus is handled by algorithms such as Proof-of-Work (PoW), Proof-of-Stake (PoS), Delegated Proof-of-Stake (DPoS), and Byzantine Fault Tolerance (BFT), depending on the blockchain platform [38, 41]. So far, there are many blockchain platforms, but the most popular are Bitcoin [21], Ethereum [42], and Hyperledger [43]. Blockchain can be public, private, or consortium, and its access can be permissionless or permissioned [36, 38]. A public blockchain, sometimes called permissionless, is free for anyone to join the network, read or write to the ledger, validate transactions, and mine the blocks [44, 45]. A private blockchain, also called permissioned, is owned by a single organization that is responsible for managing the blockchain and controlling access, and reading and writing the ledger [45]. Unlike private and public, a consortium blockchain is owned by a group of organizations to provide an inter-organization service. In this blockchain, the consensus process is carried out by participating organizations, while reading or writing permissions may be public, or restricted to the consortium members [40, 46].

Fig. 2. The blockchain data structure, showing block structure and interconnections.

With blockchain, strangers can transact without relying on intermediaries for trust keeping [10]. Instead, trust is ensured by asymmetric cryptographic algorithms [19], such as RSA, which is a prominent algorithm in asymmetric cryptosystems [53]. These attributes made blockchain a disruptive technology with broad applications in various domains such as finance [21], health [47], agriculture, and education [48].

C. Smart Contracts

In its first generation, blockchain was only associated with cryptocurrency, but in the second generation, smart contracts were introduced to make it programmable and applicable beyond cryptocurrencies [23, 49]. Smart contracts are computer programs (codes) stored on the blockchain that run automatically when the required conditions are met [33, 35, 50-51]. The concept of smart contracts, though recently

popularized in blockchain applications, was first introduced in 1997 [52]. Typically, all blockchains contain smart contracts as built-in scripts to execute their transaction logic [34]. However, most blockchains, such as Bitcoin, offer very limited programmability. Ethereum blockchain is a pioneer in supporting Turing-Complete smart contracts that can perform general-purpose programming [32, 35, 53], as it provides a dedicated high-level programming language and an execution environment named Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM) [32-33, 35, 53-54]. In Ethereum, smart contracts are created by nodes through a special transaction, and they are assigned a unique address on the blockchain [55]. Similarly, they are executed only when triggered by a transaction directed at them through their address, specifying the input data and the function to be called [37, 55]. They are executed independently and exactly as programmed without the possibility of censorship, falsification, or interference by third parties [46]. The introduction of smart contracts has enabled blockchain to handle more complex business constraints and promoted its application to domains other than cryptocurrency. The core functionalities of the proposed blockchain-based conceptual model in this study, such as the issuance, revocation, and verification of certificates, are demonstrated using smart contracts. Smart contracts are also used to manage the registration, deregistration, and access control of different roles involved in the model.

D. InterPlanetary File System (IPFS)

Although blockchain provides useful properties, its computational power and storage space remain limited and expensive [1, 35, 37]. For that reason, it is common practice to store raw data off-chain while storing only a few critical data, such as hashes and meta-data on the chain [35]. To address this need, several off-chain data storage solutions have been developed, including IPFS, Swarm, Sia, and StorJ [56]. Of all, IPFS [57] is the most popular and widely used. IPFS is a decentralized and secure content-addressable file storage system that distributes stored contents among nodes in a P2P network [33, 58]. IPFS is content addressable in the sense that each content (file), locally stored in a peer node, is hashed and the generated hash is used as a content identifier (CID) [33, 58]. During retrieval, the content is located by specifying its CID rather than its location [58]. The proposed model uses IPFS for the storage of raw certificates, equivalent statements, issuer profile information, and other complementary information to relieve the blockchain from storage overhead.

III. RELATED WORKS

A. Non-Blockchain-based Related Works

Before the advent of blockchain, scholars and practitioners used non-blockchain-based techniques to improve the verification of educational certificates and alleviate associated fraud [59]. These methods came in a variety of ways and used different techniques, such as OCR [60], hash [61], 2D barcode [62], QR codes [63], RFID [64], NFC [65], web applications [7], and mobile applications [66]. In [13], poor verification methods were shown to fail to detect forgeries. Furthermore, since the verification process left loopholes for bad actors to use fake certificates, the digitization of the verification process was suggested at all levels of education. In [66], QR codes and

web and mobile applications were used to develop a certificate verification system for Semarang University in Indonesia. This approach formulated a fingerprint of the certificate information, which was encoded along with a URL link to the web application as a QR code. For verification, the verifiers scan a QR code using their smartphone to redirect to the web app where information is stored for comparison. In [7, 67], challenges in verifying educational credentials against counterfeits were found, and web-based applications were developed to authenticate credentials. These approaches were somewhat similar, as they both involved centralized databases of student records and provided an Application Programming Interface (API) for recruiters (e.g. employers) to access them via a web-based application. However, these techniques are manual or semi-automated, making them inefficient for certificate verification and forgery prevention [59]. Furthermore, most of them depend on conventional centralized database systems. As a result, they are vulnerable to a single point of failure [10, 26, 56], internal [4, 68] and other security threats.

B. Blockchain-based Related Works

Several initiatives and research efforts have been presented on utilizing blockchain for educational certificate verification and forgery prevention. Blockcerts [69] is one of the early blockchain-based initiatives on certification. This is an open standard platform based on Bitcoin that enables educational institutions to implement blockchain-based solutions for issuing, sharing, and verifying certificates. However, as noted in [70], it cannot verify the issuing institutions, as it does not check if the public key is owned by the issuer, leaving a chance for fake institutions to issue certificates. Moreover, it does not implement on-chain certificate revocation [71]. In 2017, the University of Nicosia (UNIC) used Blockcerts and became the first institution to issue all academic certificates on the Bitcoin blockchain [72]. In their solution, a PDF certificate is hashed using SHA-256, and the digest is stored on the blockchain so that third parties can access it to verify the certificate. This solution is limited to a single university and inherits Blockcerts limitations. Capitalizing on the same Blockcerts, Malta is said to be the first country to issue educational certificates on the blockchain at a national level [73]. This solution is said to operate at the national level, but its technical details have not been presented. However, the use of Blockcerts may embed its limitations.

Many other solutions followed with some improvements. For example, using the ARK blockchain, EduCTX was proposed in [36] to improve the issuance, storage, sharing and verification of credits accrued from higher education. The system is based on the European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS) and represents ECTS credits as ECTX tokens on the blockchain. In [1], Blockchain for Education was proposed using the public Ethereum blockchain, smart contracts, IPFS, and proof-of-stake to issue, share, and validate certificates. In [26], the University of Zurich BlockChain (UZHBC) was proposed for certificate verification, using the public Ethereum blockchain and smart contracts. In [10], a comprehensive blockchain-based solution, called Cerberus, was presented for the verification of higher

education certificates, combining the Ethereum blockchain with QR codes to improve usability and using on-chain smart contracts to improve certificate revocation. Other similar solutions, such as SmartCert [74], VECefblock [38], and Educ-Dapp [37], were also proposed to overcome the problem of fake credentials during recruitment.

In general, these solutions were oriented to the requirements of particular educational systems. For example, VECefblock was designed following the Vietnamese education structure, UZHBC is specific for the University of Zurich, UNIC's solution is restricted to their university, and EduCTX is meant for higher education institutions that follow ECTS standards. For that reason, they cannot directly fit into solving the certification problem in the Tanzanian education system. As suggested in [26], to fully realize the potential of blockchain-based certification solutions, its implementation should be tailored to the contextual needs of a particular education system, because the education system differs from one country to another. Therefore, the proposal of this study is tailored to the setup of the Tanzanian educational certification system to address the contextual challenges correctly. Moreover, apart from issuance and verification of certificates, it incorporates regulatory authorities to manage issuing institutions, controls the role's access permissions, provides on-chain certificate revocation, uses decentralized off-chain storage, and takes into account the equivalent statements for certificates acquired abroad. The existing solutions have not included all these features, hence partially solving the certification problem.

IV. METHODOLOGY

Due to the multidisciplinary nature of this study, a combination of methods was used. The first part describes the methods used to uncover certification problems in Tanzania, while the second describes the design of the conceptual model.

A. Uncovering the Certification Problems

1) Research Approach and Design

Quantitative and qualitative research approaches were used to provide a deeper and broader understanding of the certification problem. The case study design strategy was adopted, as suggested in [75-76], to thoroughly investigate the challenges of certificate verification in the case of Tanzania.

2) Research Setting and Participants

This study was conducted in the Tanzanian context because it is intended to uncover and address the challenges of certificate verification in Tanzania. The study focused on secondary, vocational, technical, and university certificates, which are the most used in applications for jobs, admissions, and other purposes. Information on certification issues was gathered from certificate issuers (educational institutions), recruiters (employers and admission officers), and regulators of educational institutions.

3) Sample Size and Sampling Technique

A total of 137 participants were involved, including 65 issuers, 67 certificates, and 5 regulators. Cochran's formula for the unknown population and its adjustment formula for the

finite population were used to determine the sample size for issuers and recruiters, whereas, for regulators, a complete enumeration was used [77-78]. The respondents were selected using a nonprobabilistic sampling technique called Stratified Purposive Sampling [79-80] to focus on cases that are rich in desired information and can accommodate the heterogeneity of the research population (certification stakeholders), which is divided into different groups [81].

4) Data Collection and Analysis

This study adopted methodological and data source triangulation techniques in data collection to ensure the validity and reliability of its findings, as suggested by [82-83]. Data were collected from multiple certification stakeholders using questionnaires and interviews, supplemented by observations and documentary reviews to capture different perspectives on the certification problem in Tanzania. For data analysis, descriptive and thematic approaches were used to analyze quantitative and qualitative data, respectively.

B. Designing the Conceptual Model

The design concept of the model relies on existing knowledge from the literature and other available resources. Its construction involved the use of design modeling techniques and tools to represent and describe the structure, components, relationships, behavior, and functionality of the proposed artifact. The Unified Modeling Language (UML) [84] was used as a general guideline to inform the design, and the diagrams.net [85] diagramming tool was used for creating a visual representation of the model.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Current Verification Process and Methods

The verification process begins when recruiters receive certificates from their candidates as they submit applications via email, hand delivery, or online application systems. After receiving a certificate, the recruiters verify it using several methods, as shown in Figure 3. From the findings, 76.1% of the recruiters reach out to issuers for verification, 71.6% ask their applicants to get their certificates certified by a notary or issuer, 64.2% inspect the certificate's security features, 43.3% indicated that, apart from checking the certificates, they also examine the competence of the candidates via aptitude tests, 29.9% verify online via an API that links their online application system to issuer's centralized database, however, this is only used for secondary certificates and only applicable to few recruiters who use online application systems, 23.9% accept a certificate by a mere trust or its look without establishing concrete facts, and 4.5% verify by scanning QR codes imprinted on the certificates. The results show that the most widely used method is reaching out to issuers for verification, implying a high dependency on the issuers for verification. This dependency is attributed to the fact that the proof-of-authenticity features embedded in the certificates can only be confirmed by the issuers, and issuers are the only ones who maintain student records that can be referred to for verification of certificates. QR code scanning is the least used method because it is an emerging technology in Tanzania and only a few institutions use such codes.

Fig. 3. Verification methods used by recruiters (e.g. employers, admission officers, and others).

As mentioned above, in addition to conducting internal verification, the recruiters also consult issuers to verify certificates. Figure 4 shows that after receiving verification requests, the issuers verify using the following methods: All issuers (100%) indicated that they consult student or certificate records to match the information, 73.8% indicated that they inspect the certificate's security features, and 9.2% indicated that they scan QR codes embedded on the certificates. However, most of them use a combination of methods. The reasons that contribute to the low adoption of QR codes by recruiters are also applicable to issuers.

Fig. 4. Verification methods used by issuers (educational institutions).

B. Challenges in the Verification of Educational Certificates

Figure 5 shows the findings from the respondents who were asked to identify the challenges of verification of certificates in Tanzania, and the following are the main indicated issues.

Fig. 5. Challenges facing the current certificate verification system.

1) Manual Verification Procedures

Most of the respondents (89.8%) indicated that manual procedures are the main challenge in certificate verification. Due to the paper-based nature of certificates in Tanzania, their verification process is predominantly manual. The current process includes actions such as communication between the parties involved in the verification, and storage, sharing, recording and retrieving of information, inspection of security features, scanning of QR codes, and notarization of the certificates. Essentially, all these activities are carried out manually, without any kind of automation. According to recruiters and issuers, the verification process is burdensome, lengthy, time-consuming, costly, inefficient, and unreliable.

2) Unverifiability of Certificates

Approximately 70% of the respondents indicated that unverifiable credentials from recruiters are one of the challenges facing the verification of certificates. To protect a certificate from forgery, issuers usually incorporate physical security features such as holograms, signatures, stamps, and others to act as a tamper-proof and proof-of-authenticity. However, these features are secretly encoded by the issuers to avoid imitation, and they are the only ones who can decode them. Consequently, recruiters cannot verify the authenticity of certificates because they are unfamiliar with the features.

3) Communication Drawbacks

To reliably verify the certificate, recruiters have to seek assistance from issuers and regulators. They communicate by sending letters with certificates to be verified, which are then delivered by physical visits, postal mail, or email, while sometimes they also use phone calls to inquire for verification. As indicated by 59.9% of the respondents, current communication methods pose some serious challenges that impede the verification of certificates for fraud prevention. These methods are associated with delayed delivery of verification requests and responses. As a result, a lot of time is spent either reaching out to the institutions or waiting for verification feedback. Sometimes, the request may not be responded to. Additionally, there is a significant financial burden in facilitating physical visits and communication. For instance, an employer responded that "contacting issuers to verify certificates takes a very long time, like weeks or even months, and, worse enough, they may not respond to our requests. Physically visiting each issuing institution is not feasible because it is more expensive and time-consuming."

4) Vulnerability of Centralized Systems

The issuing institutions maintain graduate records in their registries, stored electronically in centralized computer systems along with physical storage in file cabinets. Issuers retrieve the information required from these records to print or verify certificates. Therefore, the security of these systems is crucial. However, since these systems are centralized, they are vulnerable to attacks and difficult to secure, as indicated by 40.1% of the respondents. As they act as a single point of failure, both issuers and recruiters reported several instances in which they were unable to perform verification due to system failure or unavailability. Second, they are susceptible to internal threats posed by corrupt officials, who may collude

with graduates to manipulate records and print fake certificates. Most issuers admit that it is hard to control internal system users, especially super users, from tampering with records.

5) *Certificate Revocation Issues*

Approximately 36% of the respondents expressed that an inappropriate revocation mechanism imposes significant challenges in the verification of certificates. As mentioned above, issuers can revoke a graduate certificate in case of a problem. The current revocation mechanism involves writing a letter to the graduate and issuing a public notice of the annulment. However, this approach does not provide a way to retract a certificate from the revoked person. That means that the person may continue to use it illegally despite the revocation. Public notice alone, as is currently done, is not enough, because it cannot be readily available to recruiters whenever they need to verify a certificate. As a result, most of the recruiters do not check whether a presented certificate is revoked or not, as asserted by one of the recruiters: "We have no way to tell whether the certificate is revoked or not."

6) *Disintegrated Verification Systems*

During the recruitment application, the candidates must submit several certificates acquired from different educational institutions. To verify the credentials of a single candidate, recruiters need to check with each institution, as there is no single point through which all the certificates can be verified. The process of consulting many institutions for verification is described as tedious, time-consuming, expensive, and

inefficient, especially when having many candidates to verify. Approximately 72% of the respondents pointed out this issue as one of the bottlenecks of the verification process. This fact was reinforced by one of the recruiters, who stated that "there is no common repository of graduates' information that includes data from all issuers, which recruiters could access through a single interface for verifying all the certificates. As a result, the verification of certificates becomes difficult."

7) *Dependency on Issuers for Verification*

As indicated by 76.1% of recruiters, reaching out to issuers is the most used method for verifying certificates, implying a high dependency on the issuers for verification. This overdependency on the issuers imposes some challenges to both issuers and recruiters, as indicated by 56.2% of the respondents. On the issuer side, they are overloaded by the heavy workload imposed by a large volume of verification requests they receive from recruiters across the country. On the other hand, recruiters spend a lot of time and money reaching out to issuers for verification while pending the recruitment to wait for the verification outcome.

C. *The Proposed Blockchain-based Conceptual Model*

1) *Architecture Overview*

This study proposed a model to solve the identified certificate verification challenges in Tanzania. Figure 6 shows the proposed model based on blockchain, smart contracts, IPFS, and a decentralized application.

Fig. 6. Schematic representation of a proposed blockchain-based conceptual model for the issuance and verification of educational certificates.

This model supports the issuance, revocation, and verification of certificates and equivalent statements on the blockchain. Since the proposed model aims to improve certificate verification and forgery prevention during recruitment, it focuses on certificates that are applicable during recruitment (i.e. secondary, vocational, technical, and university certificates). This model involves the same actors as in the traditional verification system, that is, a central authority responsible for establishing regulatory bodies, regulatory bodies responsible for approving issuing institutions, issuing institutions, graduates, and recruiters (employers, admission officers).

This architecture allows users to join the blockchain network through their respective front-ends on the decentralized application (DApp). The DApp intermediates the interaction between users, the blockchain, and IPFS. The DApp is powered by smart contracts that execute on the blockchain. Smart contracts are used to implement the core logic of the model, contain variables to store certificate hashes and their associated metadata, and functions and methods for handling all the operation logic over them. Contracts can be implemented using programming languages, such as Solidity, and deployed in any blockchain platform that supports smart contracts, such as Ethereum. IPFS is used as decentralized off-chain storage of files and their associated metadata. Due to the storage and computational limitations of blockchain, if everything is performed on-chain, its performance becomes poor. Therefore, shifting some of the data and activities off-chain will potentially boost the overall performance.

2) Management of User Roles and Permissions

The management of user roles and permissions is a crucial aspect of the model. This mechanism ensures that only authorized institutions can join the blockchain to issue or revoke certificates [37], and, in turn, fake institutions can be prevented from issuing certificates [86]. Furthermore, it can also provide a way for the government and its authorities to monitor the issuance of certificates [86]. Smart contracts can be programmed to provide some checks, ensuring that only users with the appropriate permissions can perform transactions in the ledger [32, 46]. Figure 7 shows a hierarchical scheme of roles in the proposed model that involves the central authority, regulators, and issuers. Graduates and recruiters are not included in this hierarchy because they only retrieve information from the ledger, which does not involve any transaction. The central authority (e.g. the Ministry of Education representing the government) will initiate the smart contracts and act as their administrator. Through smart contracts, the central authority will register the regulators (such as TCU, NACTVET, etc.), who in turn will register the issuers. Since there are different issuing institutions at different levels of education and each level has its regulatory body, the model is designed to involve several regulators, and through smart contracts' configuration, each regulator will be allowed to register its respective issuers to the blockchain. After joining the blockchain, the regulators will register their respective issuers on the blockchain and grant them permission to issue and revoke certificates. According to Tanzania regulations, apart from approving the issuers, the regulators are also

mandated to suspend or stop the issuer from issuing certificates if they fail to meet the required quality standards. Using smart contracts, the model also allows regulators to remove issuers from the blockchain when needed. Smart contracts act as the brain behind this model and contain features such as structs, mapping, and functions. The "structs" will be used for storing user information, "mapping" (a key-value data structure) will be used to associate the user's blockchain address with their stored details, and "functions" will be used to implement all the operation logic for user registration, deregistration, and permissions. To facilitate registration, a function can be implemented to accept user registration details (such as name, address, etc.) and associate them with the specific addresses on a smart contract. For deregistration, another function can be implemented to allow user removal by deleting their details from the contracts. Functions can also be implemented to define user roles and restrict access and permissions. Due to storage limitations, the blockchain only stores essential details, such as CIDs, and raw files containing issuer profile information will be stored in the IPFS. Using CIDs, recruiters will be able to retrieve the corresponding files from the IPFS, allowing them to confirm the legitimacy of the issuers during certificate verification.

Fig. 7. Identification and authorization scheme in the proposed model.

3) The Issuance Process

To issue certificates (as shown in Figure 8), registered issuers will begin by preparing digital certificates in PDF or other formats that encode the certificate's information, such as the issuer's name, student's name, student's picture, graduation date, certificate identity, award title, and grade [11, 26]. The PDF file format is more appropriate for compatibility with legacy systems because PDF documents from the Student Record Management System (SRMS), which are normally used to print paper-based certificates, may now be used as input to the proposed system. This document and other associated metadata (such as the graduate's blockchain address) are uploaded to the DApp. The DApp forwards it to IPFS, where it is hashed using a deterministic one-way cryptographic hash function to generate a unique hash value. While the raw files are stored in the IPFS, the hash value is returned to the DApp, which then pushes it to the blockchain. To achieve this, the DApp invokes the smart contract function through a transaction signed using the issuer's private key and passes the hash value as an argument [39]. The smart contract function will verify the authenticity of the transaction source, ensuring that it comes from an authorized issuer. The function then stores the hash value alongside the certificate metadata, such as its revocation status and others, in the ledger. After that, a transaction ID/hash is returned to the DApp, then to the issuer, and the issuer shares

it with the graduate along with the digital certificate. The graduate can also obtain the issued credentials on the DApp. Through the DApp, graduates will be able to retrieve, view, and download certificates. Only the hash values of the certificates and a few attributes, such as their revocation status, are stored on-chain. Real digital certificates will be stored off-chain on the IPFS.

In the blockchain, graduates are identified using their blockchain addresses, which are generated using wallets such as MetaMask. Wallets typically generate public and private keys, which are used to create the corresponding blockchain addresses [33]. In the proposed model, graduates will be able to set up their wallet accounts, through which they can generate and manage their cryptographic keys and their corresponding blockchain addresses [10]. The wallet is then connected to the DApp through which the blockchain address can be shared with the issuers to be used to issue a certificate. Each certificate hash stored on the blockchain must be affiliated with the blockchain address of the corresponding graduate. This is achievable by using the "mapping" data structure of smart contracts. To make the model applicable across different levels of education, the same blockchain address will be used at every level of education attended by the graduate to ensure that all the certificates acquired throughout his educational journey are associated with the same address.

Fig. 8. The process of issuing a certificate.

4) The Revocation Process

Issuers can also revoke a certificate. Smart contracts deployed on the blockchain are used to handle revocation logic, as they contain data structures to maintain the revocation status of certificates and functions to manage the process [32]. During

revocation (as shown in Figure 9), using the certificate information, such as its transaction ID, the authorized issuer identifies the hash of the certificate to be revoked. Then, a revocation transaction is issued that invokes the appropriate function of the smart contract to update the revocation status [1, 10]. After that, the smart contract returns the revocation information to the DApp, through which it is sent to the issuer, and the graduate is informed about the revocation of the certificate. The DApp also updates the IPFS content of the revoked certificate to reflect the current status. This mechanism will give recruiters a means of knowing whether the certificate is revoked or not by querying the certificate status through a corresponding smart contract function.

Fig. 9. The process of revoking a certificate.

5) The Verification Process

Graduates use the certificates received to apply for different opportunities, such as employment and admission to educational institutions. During the application, the graduates share the certificate along with its unique identifier/hash with the recruiters (e.g., prospective employers). This sharing can be done separately through a secure communication channel such as email, a messaging application, or other dedicated applications. As shown in Figure 10, after receiving a certificate and its unique identifier/hash from the graduate, the recruiter submits it to the DApp's verification interface and clicks the verification button to trigger the verification process. The DApp then invokes the smart contract function dedicated to the verification of certificates and passes a certificate identifier/hash as a parameter. The smart contract searches the blockchain ledger to find the matching hash and retrieves the associated certificate details. Then it returns this information to the DApp for further processing. Using the certificate hash/id obtained from the smart contracts, the DApp also retrieves the corresponding certificate files, issuer's profile information, and

other metadata from the IPFS to complement verification. This IPFS information is also returned to the DApp. The DApp performs several verification checks to validate the certificate and the verification result is presented to the recruiter, indicating whether the certificate is valid, invalid, or revoked. This includes displaying the raw certificate and issuer profile information from the IPFS for recruiters to preview. Finally, the graduate is informed of the verification result through a separate communication channel. In this way, recruiters can verify the authenticity of a certificate in terms of its provenance, integrity of its content, legitimacy of its issuer, revocation status, and impersonation of its holder.

Fig. 10. The process of verifying a certificate.

6) Handling Equivalent Statements

As stated above, according to Tanzanian regulations, educational qualifications obtained outside the country must be converted into equivalent Tanzanian qualifications. As a result, a comparable certificate is produced and issued to the graduate to be used in Tanzania, commonly known as a certificate of equivalence or equivalent statement. To comply with this requirement, the proposed model has incorporated a mechanism for issuing, revoking, and verifying equivalent statements. The process of handling these certificates is very similar to the process involved in domestically issued certificates. The only difference is that an equivalent statement is issued by the regulatory bodies (regulators) instead of the issuing institutions (issuers). To issue the equivalent statement, the regulator prepares an equivalent statement in PDF format. This document, along with other information, is uploaded to the DApp. The DApp forwards them to the IPFS, where they are hashed to generate a unique hash value. The raw files are stored in the IPFS while the hash is returned to the DApp. The DApp then sends the hash and related metadata to the blockchain's smart contract through a transaction signed using the regulator's private key. The smart contract must verify the

source of the transaction to ensure that it comes from an authorized regulator. After confirmation, the transaction is allowed, and the hash is stored in the ledger. Finally, the transaction id/hash is returned to the DApp, presented to the regulator, and the regulator shares it with the graduate along with the equivalent statement.

To revoke an equivalent statement, the regulator begins by identifying the hash of an equivalent statement to be revoked and then triggers a revocation transaction through the DApp, which invokes the smart contract to update the revocation attribute associated with the equivalent statement's hash. Subsequently, the revocation information is sent back to the DApp, through which it comes to the regulator, and the regulator informs the graduate of the revocation. Similarly, the DApp updates the IPFS content to reflect the current status. In the verification part, the recruiter submits the equivalent statement's id/hash given by the graduate to the DApp and initiates the verification process. Using the identifier/hash, the DApp retrieves the equivalent statement information from the blockchain and IPFS and performs the verification checks to authenticate the document. This includes checking its revocation status and displaying the raw equivalent statement files from the IPFS for the recruiters to preview. The verification result is then presented to the recruiter, indicating whether the equivalent statement is valid, invalid, or revoked. Finally, the graduate is informed of the verification result.

D. How the Proposed Blockchain-based Solution Addresses the Identified Verification Challenges

Most of the limitations of the current verification system in Tanzania emanate from paper certificates and manual verification procedures. This model can eliminate both of them by introducing digital certificates and automating the tasks involved in the issuance and verification process. Recruiters will be able to verify certificates by a simple search on the blockchain system and easily get reliable results in real time [10, 26], eliminating burdensome, lengthy, costly, and inefficient verification processes [2, 38]. One further problem with current paper-based certificates or certificates of equivalence is that the embedded security features (e.g. holograms, signatures, etc.), which act as proof of their authenticity, are not verifiable by the recruiters because of their unfamiliarity with them and lack of specialized tools. However, with digitally signed certificates and their metadata in the blockchain, the digital fingerprint or hash value stored on the blockchain becomes their proof of authenticity [1]. This fingerprint or hash value can be easily accessed by the recruiters to verify a certificate by a simple lookup on the blockchain, making the certificates easily verifiable [11].

The traditional verification system in Tanzania has a high dependence on issuers for the verification of certificates and equivalent statements. This means that recruiters cannot reliably verify certificates and equivalent statements without consulting the issuers. This imposes a high workload on issuers because they have to mobilize resources and dedicate time to handle verification requests, while recruiters spend a lot of time and money consulting issuers. However, the disintermediation property of the blockchain removes the dependency on central authorities [86]. Therefore, the proposed blockchain-based

solution will allow recruiters to authenticate certificates and equivalent statements on their own without relying on the issuing institutions [3, 87]. This will eliminate the need to consult the issuing institutions, speed up the verification process, reduce verification expenses, and relieve workers of work overload [3, 10-11, 26, 87]. Additionally, most institutions maintain registries or computer systems to retrieve the information required to print and verify certificates or equivalent statements. These systems are based on centralized databases in combination with some physical storage and introduce a single point of failure, are susceptible to internal threats, and internal officials may tamper with records and produce fake certificates. However, due to the decentralized and distributed nature of the blockchain, where records are replicated on all nodes in a P2P blockchain network [3], it is difficult for the system to be attacked [39], fail, or lose data [11, 26, 87]. Furthermore, the immutability, tamperproof, and transparent nature of blockchain makes it impossible for internal officers to manipulate stored records and produce fake certificates [10].

Regarding the problems caused by disintegrated verification systems, the proposed blockchain-based system can solve the problem by allowing all certificates, including equivalent statements, to be issued on a common platform from which all recruiters can verify them through a single interface [38, 88]. In so doing, even hundreds of certificates and equivalent statements can be verified effortlessly, in a matter of minutes, and with less cost. In traditional verification systems, as found in the case of Tanzania, it is difficult for issuers to revoke a certificate or an equivalent statement and for recruiters to examine if it is revoked or not. In the proposed blockchain-based system, revocation can be achieved by including a revocation status in the data structure of the smart contracts deployed on the blockchain [32, 37]. Through a specific smart contract function, the status can be set to indicate that the certificate or equivalent statement is revoked [1, 10]. Therefore, anyone who tries to use a revoked certificate fraudulently will be prevented. This revocation status will be visible to recruiters during verification.

TABLE I. THE VERIFICATION CHALLENGES AND THEIR CORRESPONDING BLOCKCHAIN-BASED SOLUTIONS

Identified certificate verification challenges	A blockchain-based solution to the identified challenges
Paper-based certificates and manual verification procedures	The proposed solution introduces digital certificates and automates the verification process. The recruiters will verify a certificate or an equivalent statement by simply querying its hash on the blockchain and get results instantly.
Disintegrated certification and verification systems	The proposed solution introduces a single platform through which all certificates or equivalent statements from different education levels can be issued and a single interface through which the recruiters can verify them.
Dependency on the issuers for verification of certificates	The proposed solution leverages the disintermediation property of the blockchain that enables the recruiters to verify the authenticity of certificates and equivalent statements without relying on the issuers or regulators, removing the need to consult the issuing institutions.
Unverifiability of the current paper-based certificates	The proposed solution uses the hash value of a certificate or equivalent statement stored in the blockchain as their proof-of-authenticity. This hash value is easily verifiable by a simple lookup on the blockchain, hence making the certificates easily verifiable.
Challenges regarding communication between parties involved in the certificate verification process	With the proposed solution, communication between the parties involved in verifying certificates or equivalent statements will no longer be needed because the recruiters will verify them independently by querying their hash from the blockchain.
Vulnerability of centralized systems used to maintain certificate records	The proposed solution leverages the decentralization and distribution nature of the blockchain, where data is replicated to all nodes in a P2P network, making it resilient to attacks, failures, or data loss. In addition, its immutability property makes it secure from internal threats.
Certificate revocation issues	The proposed solution uses on-chain revocation by including a revocation status on the smart contracts deployed in the blockchain. This status can be set to indicate that the certificate is revoked and recruiters will invoke this status to tell if the certificate is revoked.

In general, apart from addressing the challenges of the current paper-based certificates, as shown in Table I, the following are the main functionalities and contributions of the proposed model:

- Addresses the certification problem at different levels of education across the country. This can be achieved by ensuring that graduates use the same blockchain address and ID throughout their educational journey and that all acquired certificates or equivalent statements are associated with them.
- Incorporates a hierarchical scheme of identification and authorization that includes the central authority, the regulators, and the issuers. Using smart contracts, the central authority registers the regulators, and the regulators register their respective issuers on the blockchain. It ensures that the entities involved in transactions are known and authorized to avoid degree mills.
- Emphasizes how to control the access permissions of different roles involved in the system. Smart contracts will be used to incorporate information about the participating entities and the rules that define their permissions.
- Introduces an on-chain revocation mechanism. Smart contracts provide a data structure that can include a revocation status variable, indicating if the certificate is revoked. Recruiters can refer to that status to know that the certificate or equivalent statement is revoked.
- Facilitates the issuance of certificates and equivalent statements on the blockchain. The process involves hashing a certificate or equivalent statement and storing its hash on the blockchain while storing the raw files and other complementary information in the IPFS.
- Provides a mechanism for third parties (recruiters) to verify certificates by directly querying the certificate's hash from

the blockchain and other complementary information from IPFS.

- Provides a mechanism for issuing and verifying foreign certificates on the blockchain using their equivalent statements. The regulators, responsible for generating equivalent statements for foreign awards, will upload these statements to the system and the hash will be stored in the blockchain for verification purposes.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This study investigated the educational certificate verification problem in Tanzania and proposed a blockchain-based conceptual model to address the identified challenges and improve the verification process of certificates and equivalent statements. The challenges facing the current verification system in Tanzania arise from manual procedures, unverifiable credentials, dependency on issuers, centralized systems, disintegrated systems, revocation, and communication-related issues. These challenges undermine the verification of certificates and equivalent statements, creating loopholes for forgeries to persist. The proposed model can solve these challenges by digitizing certificates or equivalent statements, cryptographically hashing them, and hosting their hashes on the blockchain ledgers so that third parties who wish to verify certificates or equivalent statements can simply query the blockchain. In addition, other unique contributions of this model include handling the certification problem at different levels of education, involving regulatory bodies to manage issuers of certificates, controlling access permissions of different roles involved in the system, on-chain revocation of certificates using smart contracts, and handling of the certificates acquired abroad.

In this approach, recruiters can perform verification without depending on issuers, accelerating the verification process, reducing expenses, and relieving them from the verification complexities. Unlike traditional systems, the proposed blockchain-based solution can be more reliable because it is highly secure against attacks, failures, and loss of records. It also includes an efficient mechanism to revoke a certificate or equivalent statement and inform recruiters. Most importantly, it is presumed that this model will positively contribute to the efforts to prevent certificate fraud. Although the proposed model is tailored to the Tanzanian qualifications system, it can be assimilated to other countries with similar educational structures that face the same challenges.

The primary goal of this study was not to provide a full implementation of a blockchain-based system but to unveil the challenges associated with the certificate verification process based on ground truth data from the Tanzanian setting and provide a detailed conceptual design of a blockchain-based model, underlining how it can address these problems. However, considering the need to demonstrate its applicability, the proposed conceptual model will be implemented to evaluate its viability in the issuance and verification of certificates for the detection of counterfeits. To be specific, a prototype or proof-of-concept based on the underlined scheme will be developed and deployed on a blockchain platform, such as Ethereum, that supports smart contracts. Finally, it will be

evaluated and validated to demonstrate its performance from a practical point of view.

REFERENCES

- [1] W. Gräther, S. Kolvenbach, R. Ruland, J. Schütte, C. Torres, and F. Wendland, "Blockchain for Education: Lifelong Learning Passport," *ERCIM-Blockchain 2018: Blockchain Engineering: Challenges and Opportunities for Computer Science Research*, 2018.
- [2] A. Grech and A. F. Camilleri, *Blockchain in Education*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2017.
- [3] O. S. Saleh, O. Ghazali, and M. E. Rana, "Blockchain based framework for educational certificates verification," *Journal of critical reviews*, vol. 7, no. 03, pp. 79–84, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.31838/jcr.07.03.13>.
- [4] R. H. Sayed, "Potential of blockchain technology to solve fake diploma problem," MSc Thesis, University of Juvaskyla, Juvaskyla, Finland, 2019.
- [5] M. E. Effiong, "A Framework for the Adoption of Blockchain Technology in Academic Certificate-Verification Systems: A Case Study in Nigeria," MSc Thesis, Tallinn University of Technology, Tallinn, Estonia, 2020.
- [6] J. Hallak and M. Poisson, *Corrupt schools, corrupt universities: what can be done?* Paris: International Institute for Educational Planning, 2007.
- [7] P. Obilikwu, K. Usman, and K. D. Kwaghtyo, "A Generic Certificate Verification System for Nigerian Universities," *International Journal of Computer Science and Mobile Computing*, vol. 8, no. 10, pp. 137–148, Oct. 2019.
- [8] Eyal Ben Cohen and R. Winch, *Diploma and Accreditation Mills: New Trends in Credential Abuse*. London, UK: Verifile Limited and Accredibase, 2011.
- [9] A. Ezell and John Bear, *Degree Mills: The Billion-Dollar Industry That Has Sold Over a Million Fake Diplomas*. New York, NY, USA: Prometheus Books, 2012.
- [10] A. Tariq, H. Binte Haq, and S. T. Ali, "Cerberus: A Blockchain-Based Accreditation and Degree Verification System," *IEEE Transactions on Computational Social Systems*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 1503–1514, Dec. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCSS.2022.3188453>.
- [11] O. Ghazali and O. S. Saleh, "A Graduation Certificate Verification Model via Utilization of the Blockchain Technology," *Journal of Telecommunication, Electronic and Computer Engineering (JTEC)*, vol. 10, no. 3–2, pp. 29–34, Sep. 2018.
- [12] "Student grades believed to be hacked at University of Regina - Regina | Globalnews.ca." *Global News*. <https://globalnews.ca/news/3790701/student-grades-believed-to-be-hacked-at-university-of-regina/>.
- [13] P. Sengati and E. Kitinya, "An inquiry on strategies to mitigate fake certificates: a case of Tanzania | International Journal of Development Research (IJDR)," *International Journal of Development Research*, vol. 8, Dec. 2018, Art. no. 14781.
- [14] G. Grolleau, T. Lakhal, and N. Mzoughi, "An introduction to the Economics of Fake Degrees," *Journal of Economic Issues*, vol. 42, no. 3, pp. 673–693, 2008.
- [15] I. Gowhar, "Degree certificate racket thrives in Bengaluru," *The Hindu*, Jun. 22, 2017.
- [16] "Your Business is your Business: Fake certificates in TZ economic equation," *The Citizen*, Mar. 30, 2021. <https://www.thecitizen.co.tz/tanzania/magazines/your-business-is-our-business-fake-certificates-in-tz-economic-equation-2590982>.
- [17] E. C. Garwe, "Qualification, Award and Recognition Fraud in Higher Education in Zimbabwe," *Journal of Studies in Education*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 119–135, Apr. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.5296/jse.v5i2.7456>.
- [18] P. K. Rangi and S. Aithal, "A Study on Blockchain Technology as a Dominant Feature to Mitigate Reputational Risk for Indian Academic Institutions and Universities," *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 275–284, Dec. 2020.
- [19] P. De Filippi, M. Mannan, and W. Reijers, "Blockchain as a confidence machine: The problem of trust & challenges of governance," *Technology*

- in Society*, vol. 62, Aug. 2020, Art. no. 101284, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2020.101284>.
- [20] I. Purdon and E. Erturk, "Perspectives of Blockchain Technology, its Relation to the Cloud and its Potential Role in Computer Science Education," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 2340–2344, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1629>.
- [21] S. Nakamoto, "Bitcoin: A Peer-to-Peer Electronic Cash System." <https://bitcoin.org/bitcoin.pdf>.
- [22] N. K. Al-Shammari, T. H. Syed, and M. B. Syed, "An Edge – IoT Framework and Prototype based on Blockchain for Smart Healthcare Applications," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7326–7331, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4245>.
- [23] R. Q. Castro and M. Au-Yong-Oliveira, "Blockchain and Higher Education Diplomas," *European Journal of Investigation in Health, Psychology and Education*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 154–167, Mar. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ejihpe11010013>.
- [24] M. J. Mwandosya and M. L. Luhanga, "Blockchain: A Disruptive and Transformative Technology of the Fourth Industrial Revolution," *Business Management Review*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 16–31, Mar. 2021.
- [25] A. Preukschat and D. Reed, *Self-Sovereign Identity*. Shelter Island, NY, USA: Manning Publications, 2021.
- [26] J. Gresch, B. Rodrigues, E. Scheid, S. S. Kanhere, and B. Stiller, "The Proposal of a Blockchain-Based Architecture for Transparent Certificate Handling," in *Business Information Systems Workshops*, Berlin, Germany, 2019, pp. 185–196, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-04849-5_16.
- [27] "The Universities Act, 2005," United Republic of Tanzania, Tanzania, Jun. 2006. [Online]. Available: https://www.ilo.org/dyn/natlex/natlex4.detail?p_lang=en&p_isn=82136&p_country=TZA&p_count=270.
- [28] "Amendment of the National Council for Technical Education Act (cap. 129)," United Republic of Tanzania, Tanzania, 2021. [Online]. Available: [https://www.parliament.go.tz/polis/uploads/bills/acts/1649232323-ACT%20NO.%206%20THE%20WRITTEN%20LAWS%20\(MISCELLANEOUS%20AMENDMENTS\)%20\(NO.%204\)%20ACT,%202021.pdf](https://www.parliament.go.tz/polis/uploads/bills/acts/1649232323-ACT%20NO.%206%20THE%20WRITTEN%20LAWS%20(MISCELLANEOUS%20AMENDMENTS)%20(NO.%204)%20ACT,%202021.pdf).
- [29] "The National Examinations Council of Tanzania Act," United Republic of Tanzania, Tanzania, 2019. [Online]. Available: https://necta.go.tz/exam_formarts/NECTA_ACT_RE_2019.pdf.
- [30] "The National Education Act, 1978 (No. 25 of 1978).," United Republic of Tanzania, Tanzania, 1978. [Online]. Available: https://www.ilo.org/dyn/natlex/natlex4.detail?p_lang=en&p_isn=94089&p_country=TZA&p_count=285.
- [31] "The Vocational Education and Training Act," United Republic of Tanzania, Tanzania.
- [32] R. Xie *et al.*, "Ethereum-Blockchain-Based Technology of Decentralized Smart Contract Certificate System," *IEEE Internet of Things Magazine*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 44–50, Jun. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/IOTM.0001.1900094>.
- [33] A. M. Antonopoulos and G. W. Ph.D, *Mastering Ethereum: Building Smart Contracts and DApps*. Sebastopol, CA, USA: O'Reilly Media, Inc., 2018.
- [34] R. Paulavičius, S. Grigaitis, and E. Filatovas, "A Systematic Review and Empirical Analysis of Blockchain Simulators," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 38010–38028, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3063324>.
- [35] X. Xu *et al.*, "A Taxonomy of Blockchain-Based Systems for Architecture Design," in *2017 IEEE International Conference on Software Architecture (ICSA)*, Gothenburg, Sweden, Apr. 2017, pp. 243–252, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSA.2017.33>.
- [36] M. Turkanović, M. Hölbl, K. Košič, M. Heričko, and A. Kamišalić, "EduCTX: A Blockchain-Based Higher Education Credit Platform," *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 5112–5127, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2789929>.
- [37] A. W. S. Abreu, E. F. Coutinho, and C. I. M. Bezerra, "A Blockchain-based Architecture for Query and Registration of Student Degree Certificates," in *Proceedings of the 14th Brazilian Symposium on Software Components, Architectures, and Reuse*, New York, NY, USA, Jul. 2020, pp. 151–160, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3425269.3425285>.
- [38] B. M. Nguyen, T.-C. Dao, and B.-L. Do, "Towards a blockchain-based certificate authentication system in Vietnam.," *PeerJ Computer Science*, vol. 6, pp. e266–e266, Mar. 2020.
- [39] E. Leka and B. Selimi, "BCERT – A Decentralized Academic Certificate System Distribution Using Blockchain Technology," *International Journal on Information Technologies & Security*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 103–118, 2020.
- [40] O. Dib, K. L. Brousmiche, A. Durand, E. Thea, and E. Ben Hamida, "Consortium blockchains: Overview, applications and challenges," *International Journal On Advances in Telecommunications*, 2018, [Online]. Available: <https://hal.science/hal-02271063>.
- [41] C. Fan, S. Ghaemi, H. Khazaei, and P. Musilek, "Performance Evaluation of Blockchain Systems: A Systematic Survey," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 126927–126950, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3006078>.
- [42] V. Buterin, "Ethereum: A Next-Generation Smart Contract and Decentralized Application Platform.," 2014.
- [43] E. Elrom, "Hyperledger," in *The Blockchain Developer: A Practical Guide for Designing, Implementing, Publishing, Testing, and Securing Distributed Blockchain-based Projects*, E. Elrom, Ed. Berkeley, CA, USA: Apress, 2019, pp. 299–348.
- [44] N. Elisa, L. Yang, F. Chao, N. Naik, and T. Boongoen, "A Secure and Privacy-Preserving E-Government Framework Using Blockchain and Artificial Immunity," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 8773–8789, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3239814>.
- [45] M. Aamir, R. Qureshi, F. A. Khan, and M. Huzaifa, "Blockchain Based Academic Records Verification in Smart Cities," *Wireless Personal Communications*, vol. 113, no. 3, pp. 1397–1406, Aug. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11277-020-07226-0>.
- [46] C. S. Hsu, S. F. Tu, and P. C. Chiu, "Design of an e-diploma system based on consortium blockchain and facial recognition," *Education and Information Technologies*, vol. 27, no. 4, pp. 5495–5519, May 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-021-10840-5>.
- [47] K. Rajeshkumar, C. Ananth, and N. Mohananthini, "Blockchain-Assisted Homomorphic Encryption Approach for Skin Lesion Diagnosis using Optimal Deep Learning Model," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 10978–10983, Jun. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5594>.
- [48] M. Krichen, M. Ammi, A. Mihoub, and M. Almutiq, "Blockchain for Modern Applications: A Survey," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 14, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 5274, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22145274>.
- [49] P. Mukherjee and C. Pradhan, "Blockchain 1.0 to Blockchain 4.0—The Evolutionary Transformation of Blockchain Technology," in *Blockchain Technology: Applications and Challenges*, S. K. Panda, A. K. Jena, S. K. Swain, and S. C. Satapathy, Eds. Cham, Switzerland: Springer International Publishing, 2021, pp. 29–49.
- [50] H. Taherdoost, "Smart Contracts in Blockchain Technology: A Critical Review," *Information*, vol. 14, no. 2, Feb. 2023, Art. no. 117, <https://doi.org/10.3390/info14020117>.
- [51] X. (Brian) Wu, Z. Zou, and D. Song, *Learn Ethereum: Build your own decentralized applications with Ethereum and smart contracts*. Birmingham, UK: Packt Publishing Ltd, 2019.
- [52] N. Szabo, "Formalizing and Securing Relationships on Public Networks," *First Monday*, Sep. 1997, <https://doi.org/10.5210/fm.v2i9.548>.
- [53] D. Čeke, S. Kunosić, and N. Buzadija, "Smart Contract execution costs optimisation on blockchain network," in *2022 45th Jubilee International Convention on Information, Communication and Electronic Technology (MIPRO)*, Opatija, Croatia, Feb. 2022, pp. 1442–1447, <https://doi.org/10.23919/MIPRO5190.2022.9803805>.
- [54] L. M. Palma, M. A. G. Vigil, F. L. Pereira, and J. E. Martina, "Blockchain and smart contracts for higher education registry in Brazil," *International Journal of Network Management*, vol. 29, no. 3, 2019, Art. no. e2061, <https://doi.org/10.1002/nem.2061>.

- [55] S. Peyrott, "An Introduction to Ethereum and Smart Contracts: Bitcoin & The Blockchain," *Auth0 - Blog*. <https://auth0.com/blog/an-introduction-to-ethereum-and-smart-contracts>.
- [56] N. Nizamuddin, K. Salah, M. Ajmal Azad, J. Arshad, and M. H. Rehman, "Decentralized document version control using ethereum blockchain and IPFS," *Computers & Electrical Engineering*, vol. 76, pp. 183–197, Jun. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compeleceng.2019.03.014>.
- [57] J. Benet, "IPFS - Content Addressed, Versioned, P2P File System." arXiv, Jul. 14, 2014, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1407.3561>.
- [58] D. Oliveira, M. Rahouti, A. Jaesim, N. Siasi, and L. Ko, "Can the Inter Planetary File System Become an Alternative to Centralized Architectures?," in *Human Interaction, Emerging Technologies and Future Systems V*, 2022, pp. 597–604, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-85540-6_75.
- [59] O. S. Saleh, O. Ghazali, and Qusay Al Maatouk, "Graduation Certificate Verification Model: A Preliminary Study," *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, vol. 10, no. 7, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.14569/IJACSA.2019.0100777>.
- [60] M. Warasart and P. Kuacharoen, "Paper-based Document Authentication using Digital Signature and QR Code," presented at the 4th International Conference on Computer Engineering and Technology (ICCET 2012), 2012.
- [61] H. A. Ahmed and J.-W. Jang, "Higher Educational Certificate Authentication System Using QR Code Tag," *International Journal of Applied Engineering Research*, vol. 12, no. 20, pp. 9728–9734, 2017.
- [62] M. H. Eldefrawy, K. Alghathbar, and M. K. Khan, "Hardcopy Document Authentication Based on Public Key Encryption and 2D Barcodes," in *2012 International Symposium on Biometrics and Security Technologies*, Taipei, Taiwan, Mar. 2012, pp. 77–81, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISBAST.2012.16>.
- [63] A. Singhal and R. S. Pavithr, "Degree Certificate Authentication using QR Code and Smartphone," *International Journal of Computer Applications*, vol. 120, no. 16, pp. 38–43, Jun. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.5120/21315-4303>.
- [64] S. Singh, "RFID Enabled Secure Certificate," *International Journal of Science and Research*, vol. 4, no. 5, pp. 1910–1915, 2013.
- [65] Y. Y. Hunegnaw and P. Bagane, "NFC based Anti-Counterfeiting Scheme for Certificates Identification and Verification in offline environment by using RSA digital Signature," *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*, vol. 118, no. 24, 2018.
- [66] Henny Indriyawati, Titin Winarti, and Vensy Vydia, "Web-based document certification system with advanced encryption standard digital signature," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 22, no. 1, Apr. 2021.
- [67] J. M. Muthoni, "E-verification-A case of academic testimonials," MSc Thesis, University of Nairobi, Kenya, 2015.
- [68] G. Caldarelli and J. Ellul, "Trusted Academic Transcripts on the Blockchain: A Systematic Literature Review," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 11, no. 4, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 1842, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11041842>.
- [69] M. M. L. L. Initiative, "Blockcerts-An Open Infrastructure for Academic Credentials on the Blockchain," MIT Media Lab Learning Initiative, Oct. 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://medium.com/mit-media-lab/blockcerts-an-open-infrastructure-for-academic-credentials-on-the-blockchain-899a6b880b2f>.
- [70] M. Baldi, F. Chiaraluce, M. Kodra, and L. Spalazzi, "Security analysis of a blockchain-based protocol for the certification of academic credentials." arXiv, Oct. 10, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1910.04622>.
- [71] F. R. Vidal, F. Gouveia, and C. Soares, "Blockchain Application in Higher Education Diploma Management and Results Analysis," *Advances in Science, Technology and Engineering Systems Journal*, vol. 5, no. 6, pp. 871–882, Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.25046/aj0506104>.
- [72] "University of Nicosia is the First University in the World to Publish Diplomas of All Graduating Students on the Blockchain," *University of Nicosia*, Jul. 31, 2023. <https://www.unic.ac.cy/university-of-nicosia-is-the-first-university-in-the-world-to-publish-diplomas-of-all-graduating-students-on-the-blockchain/>.
- [73] "Malta is first country to put education certificates on blockchain," *MaltaToday.com.mt*. http://www.maltatoday.com.mt/news/national/93148/malta_is_first_country_to_put_education_certificates_on_blockchain.
- [74] T. Kanan, A. T. Obaidat, and M. Al-Lahham, "SmartCert BlockChain Imperative for Educational Certificates," in *2019 IEEE Jordan International Joint Conference on Electrical Engineering and Information Technology (JEEIT)*, Amman, Jordan, Apr. 2019, pp. 629–633, <https://doi.org/10.1109/JEEIT.2019.8717505>.
- [75] C. Wohlin, "Case Study Research in Software Engineering—It is a Case, and it is a Study, but is it a Case Study?," *Information and Software Technology*, vol. 133, May 2021, Art. no. 106514, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infsof.2021.106514>.
- [76] J. Gustafsson, "Single case studies vs. multiple case studies: A comparative study."
- [77] A. S. Singh and M. B. Masuku, "Sampling techniques & determination of sample size in applied statistics research: An overview," *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, vol. 2, no. 11, Nov. 2014.
- [78] W. G. Cochran, *Sampling techniques*. Hoboken, NJ, USA: John Wiley & Sons, 1977.
- [79] K.-S. Kim, "Methodology of Non-probability Sampling in Survey Research," *American Journal of Biomedical Science & Research*, vol. 15, no. 6, Mar. 2022 Art. no. 616.
- [80] M. Shaheen, S. Pradhan, and Ranajee, "Sampling in Qualitative Research," in *Qualitative Techniques for Workplace Data Analysis*, Hershey, PA, USA: IGI Global, 2019, pp. 25–51.
- [81] D. Lakens, "Sample Size Justification," *Collabra: Psychology*, vol. 8, no. 1, Mar. 2022, Art. no. 33267, <https://doi.org/10.1525/collabra.33267>.
- [82] P. Runeson, M. Host, A. Rainer, and B. Regnell, *Case Study Research in Software Engineering: Guidelines and Examples*. Hoboken, NJ, USA: John Wiley & Sons, 2012.
- [83] S. J. Tracy, *Qualitative Research Methods: Collecting Evidence, Crafting Analysis, Communicating Impact*. Hoboken, NJ, USA: John Wiley & Sons, 2019.
- [84] "Unified Model Language." <http://www.uml.org/>.
- [85] "Draw.io." <https://app.diagrams.net/>.
- [86] V. W. Jonnalagadda Aswani Kumar Cherukuri, Kathiravan Srinivasan, Annapurna, "CryptoCert: A Blockchain-Based Academic Credential System," in *Recent Trends in Blockchain for Information Systems Security and Privacy*, Boca Raton, FL, USA: CRC Press, 2021.
- [87] G. Capece, N. Levialdi Ghiron, and F. Pasquale, "Blockchain Technology: Redefining Trust for Digital Certificates," *Sustainability*, vol. 12, no. 21, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 8952, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12218952>.
- [88] C. Turcu, C. Turcu, and I. Chiuchisan, "Blockchain and its Potential in Education." arXiv, Mar. 05, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1903.09300>.

Big Data in Education: Students at Risk as a Case Study

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ABSTRACT

This paper analyzes various machine learning algorithms to predict student failure in a specific educational dataset and a specific environment. The paper handles the prediction of student failure given the students' grades, course difficulty level, and GPA, differing from most of the provided studies in the literature, where focus is given to the surrounding environment. The main aim is to early detect students at risk of academic underperformance and implement specific interventions to enhance their academic outcomes. A diverse set of eleven Machine Learning (ML) algorithms was used to analyze the dataset. The data went through preprocessing, and features were engineered to effectively capture essential information that may impact students' academic performance. A meticulous process for model selection and evaluation was utilized to compare the algorithms' performance with regard to metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, F-score, specificity, and balanced accuracy. Our results demonstrate significant variability in the performance of the different algorithms, with Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) showing the highest overall performance, followed closely by Gradient Boosting Classifier (GBC), Neuro-Fuzzy, and Random Forest (RF). The other algorithms exhibit varying performance levels, with the Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) showing the weakest results in recall and F-score. Educational institutions can use the insight gained from this study to make data-driven decisions and design targeted interventions to help students at risk succeed academically. Furthermore, the methodology presented in this paper can be generalized and applied to other educational datasets for similar predictive purposes.

Keywords-machine learning algorithms; big data; accuracy; F-score; precision

I. INTRODUCTION

The concept of big data involves collecting a significant amount of data within a specific domain [1-19], spanning various areas like customer data in stores, digital library publications, and more. Big data are categorized into big media data [1] and big business data. Both industry and academia have shown a keen interest in exploring big data methodologies and their impact on different sectors due to their potential contribution to organizational profitability and productivity. Big data exhibits several defining characteristics, often referred to as the 5 Vs: volume, velocity, value, veracity, and variety [2]. Volume refers to the sheer amount of data, which can pose challenges in processing and storage. Veracity encompasses data quality, distinguishing between data in motion and data at rest. Value highlights data's significance within a system. Veracity pertains to data quality, ensuring it's free from noise. Variety pertains to data's structural diversity. For instance, humidity sensor data differ from alarm system data, which must be considered in the analysis phase.

The applications of big data are diverse. Call centers [3] gather extensive data that aligns with the 5 Vs, enhancing customer experiences and optimizing product

recommendations. Information technology companies utilize logs to predict hacking attempts and network resource demands [2]. Scientists employ big data to identify valuable publications [3]. Each application involves three main stages: gathering, processing, and mining [4]. Data gathering utilizes stored data, which are then formatted for streamlined mining. Data mining algorithms like decision trees [1] and Bayesian methods [1] unravel relationships between raw data and external outcomes. Data analysis in big data presents a challenge, but it is not the only one. Various challenges and issues must be addressed in big data, such as managing large data volumes, ensuring data privacy, storing vast amounts of data, visualizing data, scheduling jobs, and maintaining fault tolerance. These challenges are distinct and require specific attention.

This paper focuses on a significant application within the education sector, specifically addressing student performance prediction. The collection of large amounts of student grade data at the end of a semester presents an opportunity for utilizing big data to enhance students' final course marks. The study aims to provide early warnings for students who might be at risk of failing a course based on their early assessment results. Predicting student failure and performance is a vital aspect of education research. Employing predictive analytics

techniques enables the identification of students prone to academic underachievement, allowing timely interventions and support. This has far-reaching benefits, including improving education quality, student retention, dropout rates, and overall academic achievements. In addition to the mentioned points, the investigation into student performance prediction offers implications for various aspects of the education system [19]:

- **Personalized learning:** Accurate performance prediction facilitates tailored learning approaches, adapting teaching methods and materials to individual student needs. This can enhance engagement, motivation, and academic outcomes.
- **Early career guidance:** Performance prediction aids educators and counselors in identifying students' strengths and interests, guiding them towards suitable career paths and education decisions.
- **Parental involvement:** Reliable predictions encourage parental engagement in supporting their child's education, fostering collaboration between parents, students, and educators.
- **Policy development and implementation:** Predictive analytics informs policy-makers enabling targeted interventions to enhance education quality and resolve challenges.
- **Evaluation and accountability:** Performance prediction helps institutions assess program effectiveness, leading to continuous improvement and refined educational outcomes.
- **Research opportunities:** Exploring student performance prediction contributes to educational research in teaching methods, curriculum development, and educational technology, improving educational practices.

Investigating student failure and performance prediction extends beyond identifying students at-risk. These areas offer implications for individuals, institutions, and the society, including addressing inequality, enabling social mobility, informing policy decisions, and fostering interdisciplinary research and innovation. Accurate predictive models contribute to inclusive, equitable, and effective educational systems.

II. RELATED WORK

Educational institutions have increasingly focused on predicting student failures, leading to a surge in research using Machine Learning (ML) and data mining techniques to analyze contributing factors. The objective is to identify students at risk of failure early and intervene promptly for improved success. Various methodologies have been applied, including statistical methods, ML, and fuzzy logic. Notable studies in this field are highlighted below.

Authors in [18] introduced an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) algorithm for predicting at-risk students in self-paced online courses. Their model utilized demographic data, course enrollment, and early interaction data. Achieving an accuracy of 84.57%, the ANN outperformed baseline models, showing effectiveness in identifying and avoiding false positives. Key

predictors included age, education level, and early interaction metrics. At the same time, authors in [20] investigated emotional wellness and engagement as indicators of academic achievement in e-learning. ML revealed their significance, offering educators insights to enhance outcomes through tailored strategies. Authors in [21] explored student-athletes' causal attributions for sport and academic achievement's impact on dropout and GPA. Stable attributions correlated with better performance and lower dropout rates. Authors in [22] focused on predicting student failure in higher education using ensemble learning algorithms. Their approach achieved 89% accuracy and proposed personalized learning paths to boost academic success. Authors in [23] developed an early detection method for identifying at-risk students based on learning performance and behavior indicators, achieving 79% accuracy. Authors in [24] employed educational data mining and ML techniques to predict academic performance, with Decision Tree (DT) and ANN models achieving 82.38% and 84.57% accuracy, respectively. Authors in [25] introduced a Bayesian network model for Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) student success prediction, outperforming alternative models. Authors in [26] created a web-based platform to forecast academic achievements, using Logistic Regression (LR) and DT algorithms to attain an accuracy rate of 85%. Authors in [27] introduced the Enhanced Binary Genetic Algorithm (EBGA) for feature selection in predicting student performance, demonstrating superiority over other methods. Authors in [28] utilized supervised learning techniques, showing ANN's high accuracy in predicting student performance. Authors in [29] proposed an incremental ensemble for distance education student performance prediction, while authors in [30] focused on predicting high school dropouts using data mining techniques. Authors in [31] presented temporal models for predicting MOOC student attrition, highlighting the importance of considering temporal dynamics for accurate predictions. Table I summarizes the related works.

These studies demonstrate the diversity of approaches that have been used to predict student failure. Selection of the appropriate method depends on various factors, including the size and nature of the dataset, the availability of resources, and the desired interpretability of the results. Overall, the findings from these studies indicate that ML can offer valuable insights into predicting student failure and help educational institutions develop targeted interventions for at-risk students. However, the described papers in the related work either focus on specific or some ML algorithms or certain datasets. Also, the used datasets consider different factors around students' quizzes and final exams while they ignore other factors that affect the performance such as attendance, assignments, topics difficulty, GPA, and student level. In Saudi Arabia, the education environment is different from other countries: students do not have that many distraction factors that affect their studies. Therefore, in our study, we developed different algorithms to predict student failure using a synthetic dataset of 9,000 student records. The dataset included attendance, assignments, quiz scores, midterm and final exam scores, GPA, course difficulty levels, and students' educational levels. A voting system is used to decide on the student's performance.

TABLE I. RELATED WORK SUMMARY

Ref.	Purpose	Algorithms/ Techniques	Results/ Key Findings
[18]	Initial detection of at-risk students in self-paced education	ANNs	Effective in predicting at-risk learners
[20]	Predict the academic performance of students based on their emotional health	Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) network, Random Forest (RF), and Gradient Boosting Classifier (GBC)	96% prediction accuracy
[21]	Relation between sport dropout, GPA, and causal attributions	Latent profile analysis	Reasonable performance
[22]	Predict student failure and enable customized educational paths	Ensemble learning algorithms	Improved prediction of student failure
[23]	Early student-at-risk detection	k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN) classifier and Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA)	Good detection performance
[24]	Predicting the academic performance of students	RF, nearest neighbor, Support Vector Machines (SMVs), LR, Naïve Bayes, kNN	Classification accuracy of 70–75%
[25]	Predicting MOOC performance and improving performance	Bayesian Network	Improved MOOC performance prediction
[26]	Create an online academic performance prediction system	SVM, RF, kNN, ANN, and LR	Performance was not the target of the paper. They used mean square error to measure the performance
[27]	Improved feature selection to predict student performance	Enhanced Binary Genetic Algorithm (EBGA)	Improved prediction accuracy
[28]	Predict student academic performance using supervised learning	kNN, SVM, DT, NB, ANNs	Highest accuracy with ANNs (90%+)
[29]	Predict students' performance in distance education	Combinational incremental ensemble of classifiers	Outperforms single classifiers
[30]	Early dropout prediction using data mining	DT, ANNs, SVM	Effective in reducing dropout rates
[31]	Predict student dropout in MOOCs	Temporal models	Outperforms static models

III. METHODOLOGY

This section will elucidate the methodology of ML modeling to predict the failure of students in MOOCs. The section is divided into three key subsections: data collection, ML modeling, and model evaluation. Within the data handling subsection, this section will cover the selection of relevant features and data preprocessing to enhance the model's accuracy. The ML modeling subsection will explore various algorithms, including fuzzy logic, ANNs, neuro-fuzzy, LR, DTs, Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), kNN, Convolution Neural Networks (CNNs), and RF to determine the most suitable approach for predicting student failure. To assess the

model's performance, the model evaluation subsection provides an extensive overview of metrics, such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, specificity, and balanced accuracy. Additionally, cross-validation and hyperparameter tuning will be discussed to ensure that the model is not overfitting and is optimized for prediction accuracy. Figure 1 shows the different steps utilized in this paper.

Fig. 1. Student performance prediction proposed model.

A. Data Collection

Data collection refers to acquiring data from their source and preparing them for use in a ML model. Extraction refers to the process of retrieving information from a data source using data mining techniques. First, the data are extracted from two main sources: Blackboard and the instructors. The blackboard keeps all the student's records, therefore, most data are extracted from it. However, some missing data are gained from the course instructors. Students' GPAs are automatically extracted from another system that keeps students' official records. The dataset used for this study is obtained from the blackboard courses in different years and for different colleges taught at the University of Hail, Saudi Arabia. The provided dataset includes courses from the College of Computer Science and Engineering and other colleges from 2015 to 2020. The data follow the students from their entrance to the college to the suggested time of their graduation. Since the study is related to the student's failure prediction, the focus was on the students who could not graduate on time. Therefore, almost 50% of the dataset under study has failed students' records. The data were stored in CSV format, which can be accessed on a local machine. The experiment was conducted in a Jupyter notebook, and the data were processed using Python. The total number of records is 9,000. The dataset attributes are shown in Table II. In order to carry out supervised experiments using this dataset, the target column selected to determine student performance was the Result score (pass/fail) of the course, as it is commonly preferred. The Result score is calculated based on a combination of the Midterm exam (25%), Classwork (2 quizzes, 20% weightage), Assignments (10% weightage), Attendance (10% weightage), and the Final Exam (35% weightage). The GPA score was classified into two categories: (1) Pass, for scores greater than or equal to 60, and (2) Fail, for scores less than 60.

B. Data Preprocessing and Data Cleaning

Data preprocessing involves extracting the relevant information from the target dataset that is required for the ML model. Records with inconsistent values were removed from the data set, such as samples with high grades but very low attendance time. This restriction is applied because the students are allowed only 25% absences from the semester lectures. As a result, the data of 9,000 students were evaluated in this study.

TABLE II. DATASET ATTRIBUTES AND THEIR RANGES

Attribute	Description	Type	Value
Student_ID	Student unique identifier	Numeric	1-9000
College	Student collage	String	NA
Department	Student department	String	NA
Program	Program of study within the department	String	NA
GPA	Student GPA	Numeric	1-4
Credit	Course number of credit hours	Categorical	1-5
Teacher_ID	Teacher identifier	String	NA
Level	1-8, represents the course semester	Categorical	1-4
Difficulty	The difficulty of the course		1-5
Assignments	Classwork grades, including all assignments	Numeric	10
Quiz_1	The first Quiz	Numeric	10
Quiz_2	The second Quiz	Numeric	10
Attendance	Students attendance	Numeric	10
Midterm	Course midterm grade	Numeric	25
Final	Course final grade	Numeric	35
Results	Pass or fail	Categorical	0-1

This study focuses on identifying the features that are indicative of student failure and using them to predict such events. The extracted dataset consists of time series data with no primary keys. However, to map the data to the ML model, it is necessary to group the data based on student identity, which involves assigning each student as the key. Previous research on Educational Data Mining (EDM) datasets followed a similar approach and performed grouping as a preprocessing step to structure the raw data. In this study, a similar grouping was performed. Once the data are grouped based on student identity, the learning progression data for each student can be extracted from the target dataset and stored as a preprocessed data table. Learning progression refers to the process of acquiring and mastering knowledge, skills, or competencies over a period of time. Individuals go through a sequence of educational and developmental stages as they gain a deeper understanding and mastery of a subject or skill. Learning progression typically involves the acquisition of increasingly complex concepts and skills, building on what was previously learned, and applying it to new and more challenging contexts. Learning progression can be measured and evaluated using various methods, such as classwork, midterm, final, or results, to track a learner's progress and identify areas of strength and weakness. In order to identify shifts in a student's learning progression, we analyze the topics that the student has mastered on a semester basis. This is achieved by computing the discrepancy between the student's progress on a given semester and their cumulative progress up until that the last semester, resulting in a list of topics the student has mastered in each semester. These fluctuations in a student's learning progression are then used to extract various features that our machine-learning model will utilize.

After obtaining the preprocessed data, we must proceed to clean them before utilizing them in the modeling process. Although the preprocessed data contain all the required information, they are not structured optimally for modeling as they are in a raw form. Moreover, most of the attributes in the preprocessed data are of varying data types, which makes it necessary to standardize the data type to a consistent numerical format for modeling. Through data cleaning, the preprocessed

data are transformed into a cleaned dataset that is suitable for input of the ML model. This data-cleaning process has been described in [19]. Also, we normalized the course data based on the Z-score procedure. The Z-score procedure, also known as standardization, is a statistical method used to transform a distribution of raw scores (i.e. scores on a test or other measure) into a standard normal distribution, where the mean is 0 and the standard deviation is 1. This procedure is often used in data analysis and research to compare scores across different populations, measures, or time points. The Z-score of a raw score is calculated by subtracting the mean of the distribution from the raw score and dividing the result by the standard deviation of the distribution.

$$Z = (X - \mu) / \sigma \quad (3)$$

where Z is the Z-score, X is the raw score, μ is the mean of the distribution, and σ is the standard deviation of the distribution.

Once the Z-score is calculated for each raw score in the distribution, the transformed scores can be plotted on a standard normal distribution, allowing comparisons between different distributions. The Z-score procedure has several important uses, such as identifying outliers, comparing scores on different measures or tests, and determining the proportion of scores that fall within a certain range of values. However, it is important to note that the Z-score procedure assumes that the distribution is normal or approximately normal and may not be appropriate for non-normal distributions.

We utilized the sklearn.feature_selection algorithm from Python to check on the best features that represent the dataset. It turns out that the best features that represent the data are (in sequence): Final, Midterm, Quiz_2, Assignments, Quiz_1, Credit, and Level. Therefore, the GPA and difficulty seem to have no effect on the prediction process, see Figure 2.

C. Machine Learning Model Optimization

We utilized various ML models previously reviewed in the background section: LR, GBC, ET, DT, RF, ANNs, RNNs, CNNs, kNN, FL, and NF. The proposed model is depicted in Figure 3, where the cleaned data are fed into each ML model, and each model is optimized for the best performance based on the input data. The accuracy output of each model is then utilized in the voting module. The voting module calculates the average accuracy of the ML models producing either 0 or 1. If the average accuracy of 0 is greater than the average accuracy of 1, it is determined that the probability of a student failing is higher than the probability that he/she will pass, and vice versa.

Fig. 2. Feature effectiveness.

D. Performance Metrics

To evaluate the proposed ML models, standard criteria were utilized. Table III presents a comprehensive overview of the key performance metrics and their corresponding equations used to evaluate the classification models, particularly in binary classification tasks. It includes basic terms such as True Positive (TP), True Negative (TN), False Positive (FP), and False Negative (FN), which are the building blocks for calculating more advanced metrics. The table also outlines essential evaluation metrics, such as accuracy, precision, F-score, recall/sensitivity, specificity, and balanced accuracy. These metrics provide valuable insight into the performance of a classification model, helping identify its strengths and weaknesses and guiding further improvements in model development.

TABLE III. PERFORMANCE MEASURE CRITERIA

Term	Equation
TP	Count of true positives
TN	Count of true negatives
FP	Count of false positives
FN	Count of false negatives
Accuracy	$Accuracy = (TP + TN) / (TP + TN + FP + FN)$
Precision	$Precision = TP / (TP + FP)$
F-score	$F\text{-score} = 2 \times (Precision * Recall) / (Precision + Recall)$
Recall/Sensitivity	$Recall = TP / (TP + FN)$
Specificity	$Specificity = TN / (TN + FP)$
Balanced Accuracy	$Balanced\ Accuracy = (Recall + Specificity) / 2$

Fig. 3. Details of the proposed model.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this section, the implementation of the proposed methods is described, and the results are explained. The first model implemented is Fuzzy Logic with the membership functions presented in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Fuzzy logic membership functions: (a) Attendance, (b) Quiz 1, (c) Quiz 2, (d) Midterm, (e) Final, (f) Assignment, (g) Level, and (h) Failure probability.

In Figure 5, the performance of the Fuzzy logic classification algorithm is analyzed with including accuracy, precision, recall, F-score, specificity, and balanced accuracy. The Fuzzy algorithm attained an accuracy of 95.4%. Precision, indicating positive result accuracy, reached 88.4%, while recall, highlighting positive instance identification, was 86.4%. The F-score at 0.874 is a comprehensive performance measure. Notably, the algorithm excelled in imbalanced data with specificity at 0.974 (97.4% negative identification) and balanced accuracy at 0.919, which considers both recall and specificity. Overall, the Fuzzy algorithm showed strong classification performance with high accuracy, precision, recall, F-score, and demonstrated robustness on imbalanced data. Another implemented model, Neuro-fuzzy, displayed similar fuzzy membership functions. In Figure 6, Neuro-fuzzy exhibited high performance in accuracy, precision, recall, F-score, specificity, and balanced accuracy. Its accuracy at 0.982 signifies a high proportion of correct classifications. Precision indicated an 84.8% accurate prediction of positive outcomes. A recall of 0.971 demonstrated successful identification of positive cases. The F-score of 0.905 balances precision and recall. The algorithm's specificity at 0.983 ensured accurate negative case identification. With a balanced accuracy of 0.977, it performed well across both classes. In summary, Neuro-fuzzy proved a promising classification approach, achieving notable accuracy, precision, recall, F-score, specificity, and balanced accuracy.

Fuzzy Logic Performance

Fig. 5. Fuzzy logic performance.

Neuro Fuzzy Performance

Fig. 6. Neuro-fuzzy logic.

In terms of algorithm performance, the LR algorithm achieved an accuracy of 91%, indicating generally accurate predictions. Its precision of 0.577 suggests moderate ability to

correctly identify positive cases, while a recall of 0.174 indicates difficulty in identifying positive cases. The F-score, at 0.267, highlights relatively poor performance in identifying positive cases. However, the algorithm's specificity of 0.987 demonstrates its ability to identify negative cases. The balanced accuracy of 0.5805 reflects a moderate overall performance, indicating that the LR algorithm excels in identifying negative cases but struggles with positive cases.

On the other hand, the GBC algorithm produced impressive results, achieving an accuracy of 98.6%. The precision score of 0.983 signifies high accuracy in positive predictions. The recall score of 83.8% indicates effective identification of the positive cases. The F-score, reaching 0.905, showcases strong performance in predicting both positive and negative cases. With a specificity score of 0.999, the algorithm excelled in identifying negative cases. The balanced accuracy of 0.9185 provides an overall measure of performance across both positive and negative classes, underscoring the algorithm's remarkable capabilities.

LR Performance

Fig. 7. Linear regression performance.

Gradient Boosting Classifier Performance

Fig. 8. Gradient boosting classifier performance.

In Figure 9, the performance of the Extra Trees (ET) algorithm is illustrated, showcasing strong results. The algorithm achieved an impressive accuracy of 0.971, indicating overall effectiveness. The precision score of 0.9 and the recall score of 0.682 highlight the model's ability to identify positive cases. Despite a slightly lower F-score of 0.776, the high specificity score of 0.994 signifies accurate identification of the negative cases. The balanced accuracy score of 0.838 further

reinforces the algorithm's proficiency. In conclusion, the ET algorithm exhibits satisfying performance.

Figure 10 displays results of the DT algorithm, which achieved 96.2% accuracy, showcasing its effectiveness in accurate instance classification. With a precision of 86.8% and specificity of 98.3%, the model minimizes false-positive and false-negative errors. The recall score of 81.3% indicates a substantial identification of positive cases but leaves room for improvement. The F-score of 84% signifies a balanced trade-off between precision and recall. The balanced accuracy of 89.8% underscores the algorithm's equilibrium in recognizing positive and negative cases. Overall, the DT algorithm displays strong performance in this classification task, with potential for further enhancement.

Fig. 9. Extra trees performance.

Fig. 10. Decision tree performance.

RF in Figure 11 demonstrates strong performance. It achieved an accuracy of 98.1%, indicating that it can correctly classify a high percentage of instances. With a precision of 85.3% and specificity of 98.7%, the algorithm effectively minimizes false-positive errors while correctly identifying negative cases. The recall of 90.4% shows that the model successfully identifies most of the positive cases, and the F-score of 87.8% highlights a good balance between precision and recall. The balanced accuracy of 94.55% further emphasizes that the algorithm performs well in identifying both positive and negative cases, making it a reliable choice for this classification problem.

The ANN algorithm in Figure 12 demonstrates outstanding performance. It achieves an accuracy of 99.9%, precision of 99.3%, recall of 99.3%, F-score of 99.3%, specificity of 99.9%,

and balanced accuracy of 99.6%. These impressive results across all metrics indicate that ANNs are highly effective in identifying positive and negative cases while minimizing false positives and false negatives. The almost perfect scores in each category suggest that the ANN algorithm is well-suited for this type of problem and provides a reliable and balanced solution.

Fig. 11. Random forest performance.

Fig. 12. Artificial neural network performance.

Fig. 13. Convolution neural network performance.

In Figure 13, the CNN demonstrates exceptional performance in a classification task with 1800 samples. The CNN achieves an impressive accuracy of 99.9%, along with a precision, recall, and F-score of 99.3%. These values highlight the CNN's effectiveness in accurately identifying positive and negative cases while minimizing errors. The model's specificity of 99.9% and balanced accuracy of 99.6% further underscore its ability to classify both classes accurately, making it a top-performing classifier.

Figure 14 presents the performance of the kNN algorithm. It attains an accuracy of 96.1%, indicating a substantial number of correct classifications. However, the recall of 59.2% and F-

score of 70.6% suggest that the kNN struggles to identify positive cases compared to its strong specificity of 99.3%, which excels at identifying negative cases. With a precision of 87.5%, the algorithm keeps false-positive errors low. The balanced accuracy of 79.25% suggests a somewhat imbalanced performance, leaning toward specificity. There's potential for improvement in the kNN algorithm, particularly in identifying positive cases.

Fig. 14. kNN performance.

Fig. 15. Recurrent neural network performance.

The RNN performance, as presented in Figure 15, achieves an overall accuracy of 92.4%. While demonstrating a strong specificity of 99.9%, indicating proficient identification of negative cases, it struggles with positive case detection, exhibiting a low recall of 5.6%. Despite the 80% precision, the F-score is only 10.5%, highlighting an imbalance between precision and recall. The balanced accuracy of 52.75% underscores the algorithm's uneven performance between positive and negative case classification. In essence, the RNN algorithm's performance in this context is suboptimal, particularly evident in its challenge to identify positive cases, as evidenced by the low recall and F-score values.

A. Discussion

The given results summarized in Table IV present the performance metrics of 12 different algorithms. ANNs and CNNs exhibit the highest performance in almost all the metrics among all the algorithms. They both demonstrate an impressive 99.9% accuracy, 99.3% precision and recall, 99.3% F-score, 99.9% specificity, and 99.6% balanced accuracy. GBC ranks third in accuracy with 98.6%. It also features high precision and specificity, however, its recall is lower, leading to an F-score of 90.5% and a balanced accuracy of 91.85%. The Neuro Fuzzy algorithm has the second-highest accuracy (98.2%) and balanced accuracy (97.7%). It also shows good recall (97.1%) and F-score (90.5%), although its precision (84.8%) and specificity (98.3%) are lower compared to the top-performing models. The RF algorithm demonstrates strong performance with an accuracy of 98.1%. DT, kNN, and RNNs have relatively lower performance metrics than the top-performing models.

The ANN and CNN algorithms demonstrate the best overall performance among all the models. The GBC, Neuro-Fuzzy, and RF algorithms also perform well, but not as strongly as the ANN and CNN models. The other algorithms exhibit varying performance levels, with the LR and RNN algorithms showing the weakest results.

TABLE IV. RESULT SUMMARY

Algorithm	TP	TN	FP	FN	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F-score	Specificity	Balanced Accuracy
Fuzzy	344	1701	45	54	0.954	0.884	0.864	0.874	0.974	0.919
Neuro Fuzzy	168	1765	30	5	0.982	0.848	0.971	0.905	0.983	0.977
LR	30	1636	22	142	0.91	0.577	0.174	0.267	0.987	0.5805
GBC	119	1656	2	23	0.986	0.983	0.838	0.905	0.999	0.9185
ET	90	1658	10	42	0.971	0.9	0.682	0.776	0.994	0.838
DT	178	1554	27	41	0.962	0.868	0.813	0.84	0.983	0.898
RF	122	1644	21	13	0.981	0.853	0.904	0.878	0.987	0.9455
ANN	141	1657	1	1	0.999	0.993	0.993	0.993	0.999	0.996
CNN	141	1657	1	1	0.999	0.993	0.993	0.993	0.999	0.996
kNN	84	1646	12	58	0.961	0.875	0.592	0.706	0.993	0.7925
RNN	8	1656	2	134	0.924	0.8	0.056	0.105	0.999	0.5275

V. CONCLUSION

The current paper addresses the challenge of predicting student performance using various data such as assignment grades, quizzes, midterms, finals, and other parameters. The focus is on preemptively identifying student failure. Multiple machine learning algorithms are proposed, including Fuzzy, Neuro-Fuzzy, LR, GBC, ET, DT, RF, ANN, CNN, kNN, and RNN. These algorithms' performances are evaluated using metrics like Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F-score, Specificity,

and Balanced Accuracy. The findings reveal that ANN and CNN outperform the other models, with GBC, Neuro-Fuzzy, and RF also showing strong but less consistent results. The other algorithms exhibit varying levels of effectiveness, with LR and RNN performing poorly. The paper's innovation lies in automating accurate student performance assessment, potentially saving instructors' time and ensuring fairness. For student performance evaluation, the recommendation is to

prioritize the use of ANNs and CNNs due to their superior performance compared

REFERENCES

- [1] I. Guellil and K. Boukhalfa, "Social big data mining: A survey focused on opinion mining and sentiments analysis," in *2015 12th International Symposium on Programming and Systems (ISPS)*, Algiers, Algeria, Apr. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISPS.2015.7244976>.
- [2] S. Sharma and V. Mangat, "Technology and Trends to Handle Big Data: Survey," in *2015 Fifth International Conference on Advanced Computing & Communication Technologies*, Haryana, India, Oct. 2015, pp. 266–271, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCT.2015.121>.
- [3] F. Xia, W. Wang, T. M. Bekele, and H. Liu, "Big Scholarly Data: A Survey," *IEEE Transactions on Big Data*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 18–35, Mar. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TBDATA.2016.2641460>.
- [4] J. Zhang, X. Yao, G. Han, and Y. Gui, "A survey of recent technologies and challenges in big data utilizations," in *2015 International Conference on Information and Communication Technology Convergence (ICTC)*, Jeju, Korea, Jul. 2015, pp. 497–499, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICTC.2015.7354594>.
- [5] J. V. Gautam, H. B. Prajapati, V. K. Dabhi, and S. Chaudhary, "A survey on job scheduling algorithms in Big data processing," in *2015 IEEE International Conference on Electrical, Computer and Communication Technologies (ICECCT)*, Coimbatore, India, Mar. 2015, pp. 1–11, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICECCT.2015.7226035>.
- [6] A. Fahad et al., "A Survey of Clustering Algorithms for Big Data: Taxonomy and Empirical Analysis," *IEEE Transactions on Emerging Topics in Computing*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 267–279, Sep. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TETC.2014.2330519>.
- [7] S. Gole and B. Tidke, "A survey of big data in social media using data mining techniques," in *2015 International Conference on Advanced Computing and Communication Systems*, Coimbatore, India, Jan. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICACCS.2015.7324059>.
- [8] J. Wang, Y. Wu, N. Yen, S. Guo, and Z. Cheng, "Big Data Analytics for Emergency Communication Networks: A Survey," *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 1758–1778, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1109/COMST.2016.2540004>.
- [9] S. Yu, M. Liu, W. Dou, X. Liu, and S. Zhou, "Networking for Big Data: A Survey," *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 531–549, 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1109/COMST.2016.2610963>.
- [10] D. Ramesh, P. Suraj, and L. Saini, "Big data analytics in healthcare: A survey approach," in *2016 International Conference on Microelectronics, Computing and Communications (MicroCom)*, Durgapur, India, Jan. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MicroCom.2016.7522520>.
- [11] M. Pandey, R. Litoriya, and P. Pandey, "Mobile applications in context of big data: A survey," in *2016 Symposium on Colossal Data Analysis and Networking (CDAN)*, Indore, India, Mar. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CDAN.2016.7570942>.
- [12] M. Saberi, A. Karduck, O. K. Hussain, and E. Chang, "Challenges in Efficient Customer Recognition in Contact Centre: State-of-the-Art Survey by Focusing on Big Data Techniques Applicability," in *2016 International Conference on Intelligent Networking and Collaborative Systems (INCoS)*, Ostrava, Czech Republic, Sep. 2016, pp. 548–554, <https://doi.org/10.1109/INCoS.2016.136>.
- [13] Y. Hou, J. Xu, Y. Huang, and X. Ma, "A big data application to predict depression in the university based on the reading habits," in *2016 3rd International Conference on Systems and Informatics (ICSAI)*, Shanghai, China, Aug. 2016, pp. 1085–1089, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSAI.2016.7811112>.
- [14] R. M. Mathew and R. Gunasundari, "A Cluster-based Undersampling Technique for Multiclass Skewed Datasets," *Eng. Technol. Appl. Sci. Res.*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 10785–10790, Jun. 2023.
- [15] A. B. Rashid, R. R. I. Ikram, Y. Thamilarasan, L. Salahuddin, N. F. A. Yusof, and Z. B. Rashid, "A Student Learning Style Auto-Detection Model in a Learning Management System," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 11000–11005, Jun. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5751>.
- [16] S. Joseph, N. Mduma, and D. Nyambo, "A Deep Learning Model for Predicting Stock Prices in Tanzania," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 10517–10522, Apr. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5710>.
- [17] B. Veloso, M. A. Barbosa, H. Faria, F. S. Marcondes, D. Durães, and P. Novais, "A Systematic Review on Student Failure Prediction," in *Methodologies and Intelligent Systems for Technology Enhanced Learning, Workshops, 12th International Conference*, 2023, pp. 43–52, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-20257-5_5.
- [18] H. Waheed, S.-U. Hassan, R. Nawaz, N. R. Aljohani, G. Chen, and D. Gasevic, "Early prediction of learners at risk in self-paced education: A neural network approach," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 213, Mar. 2023, Art. no. 118868, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2022.118868>.
- [19] Nuralitasari, Z. Awang Long, and M. F. Mohd Noor, "The Predictive Learning Analytics for Student Dropout Using Data Mining Technique: A Systematic Literature Review," in *Advances in Technology Transfer Through IoT and IT Solutions*, A. Ismail, F. N. Zulkiply, Z. Awang Long, and A. Öchsner, Eds. Springer Nature Switzerland, 2023, pp. 9–17.
- [20] A. Kukkar, R. Mohana, A. Sharma, and A. Nayyar, "Prediction of student academic performance based on their emotional wellbeing and interaction on various e-learning platforms," *Education and Information Technologies*, vol. 28, no. 8, pp. 9655–9684, Aug. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-022-11573-9>.
- [21] M. Saarinen, R. Bertram, K. Aunola, J. Pankkonen, and T. V. Ryba, "Student Athletes' Causal Attributions for Sport and School Achievement in Relation to Sport Dropout and Grade Point Average," *Journal of Sport & Exercise Psychology*, vol. 45, no. 1, pp. 15–25, Feb. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1123/jsep.2022-0115>.
- [22] L. K. Smirani, H. A. Yamani, L. J. Menzli, and J. A. Boulahia, "Using Ensemble Learning Algorithms to Predict Student Failure and Enabling Customized Educational Paths," *Scientific Programming*, vol. 2022, Apr. 2022, Art. no. e3805235, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/3805235>.
- [23] T. A. Kustitskaya, A. A. Kytmanov, and M. V. Noskov, "Early Student-at-Risk Detection by Current Learning Performance and Learning Behavior Indicators," *Cybernetics and Information Technologies*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 117–133, Mar. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.2478/cait-2022-0008>.
- [24] M. Yağcı, "Educational data mining: prediction of students' academic performance using machine learning algorithms," *Smart Learning Environments*, vol. 9, no. 1, Mar. 2022, Art. no. 11, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40561-022-00192-z>.
- [25] J. Hao, J. Gan, and L. Zhu, "MOOC performance prediction and personal performance improvement via Bayesian network," *Education and Information Technologies*, vol. 27, no. 5, pp. 7303–7326, Jun. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-022-10926-8>.
- [26] D. Alboaneen, M. Almelih, R. Alsubaie, R. Alghamdi, L. Alshehri, and R. Alharthi, "Development of a Web-Based Prediction System for Students' Academic Performance," *Data*, vol. 7, no. 2, Feb. 2022, Art. no. 21, <https://doi.org/10.3390/data7020021>.
- [27] S. S. Shreem, H. Turabieh, S. Al Azwari, and F. Baothman, "Enhanced binary genetic algorithm as a feature selection to predict student performance," *Soft Computing*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 1811–1823, Feb. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00500-021-06424-7>.
- [28] M. Imran, S. Latif, D. Mehmood, and M. S. Shah, "Student Academic Performance Prediction using Supervised Learning Techniques," *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (iJET)*, vol. 14, no. 14, pp. 92–104, Jul. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v14i14.10310>.
- [29] S. Kotsiantis, K. Patriarcheas, and M. Xenos, "A combinational incremental ensemble of classifiers as a technique for predicting students' performance in distance education," *Knowledge-Based Systems*, vol. 23, no. 6, pp. 529–535, Aug. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.knsys.2010.03.010>.
- [30] C. Márquez-Vera, A. Cano, C. Romero, A. Y. M. Noaman, H. Mousa Fardoun, and S. Ventura, "Early dropout prediction using data mining: a case study with high school students," *Expert Systems*, vol. 33, no. 1, pp. 107–124, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1111/exsy.12135>.
- [31] M. Fei and D.-Y. Yeung, "Temporal Models for Predicting Student Dropout in Massive Open Online Courses," in *2015 IEEE International*

Conference on Data Mining Workshop (ICDMW), Atlantic City, NJ, USA, Aug. 2015, pp. 256–263, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDMW.2015.174>.

A Comparative Study of the Seismic Response of Different Concrete Slab Systems for a Multistory Building in Madinah

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ABSTRACT

Seismic analysis is considered as an important aspect of the design of high-rise buildings, particularly in earthquake prone areas. The structural system choice can have a considerable impact on the building seismic response. The goal of this study is to compare the seismic behavior of multiple slab systems used in a multi-story building in Saudi Arabia's Madinah region. This study's goal is to determine the most effective and efficient slab system performance in a seismic zone. The ETABS V20.3 program was used in this work to model and assess the seismic response of three different types of slab systems: flat, solid, and hollow blocks slab types. Many earthquake aspects, including story displacement, base shear, story drifts, column forces, and bending moments, are estimated for each system. The study examines and assesses each system's seismic response, and the conclusions are given and discussed. According to the findings, the choice of slab system has a considerable impact on the seismic reaction of the building. The hollow block system has the least base shear value and bending moments, while the flat slab system has the greatest. The values in the solid slab system are in the middle. In terms of story displacement and column forces, the study additionally indicates that the hollow block type system performs effectively in terms of story drifts, however, the solid slab system outperforms the others. The study's findings can assist designers and engineers to determine the best slab system for multistory buildings in seismic-prone areas by providing important insight and suggestions.

Keywords-story displacement; base shear; column forces; story drift

I. INTRODUCTION

Design and rapid urbanization, driven by increasing population densities, have increased the construction of high-rise structures to meet the growing demand for residential and commercial areas [1]. While these tall structures represent architectural achievements, they are also vulnerable to a wide range of natural and anthropogenic hazards. Seismic disturbances stand out as one of the most crucial challenges [2]. The shear uncertainty and force of earthquakes can wreak

havoc, resulting in casualties, property destruction, and far-reaching economic consequences [3, 19]. High-rise structures are intrinsically more vulnerable to the dynamic and uncertain forces generated during seismic occurrences due to their tall stature and significant mass [4, 20]. If not treated properly, the lateral and vertical forces created during such disturbances can cause large strains, potentially leading to structural deficiencies or even catastrophic collapses [5, 21]. As a result, the importance of seismic analysis and design is paramount, as they are critical in guaranteeing the structural integrity and

safety of these structures [6, 22]. The slab system and design are essential to this seismic design approach [8, 23]. The slab, as a fundamental horizontal structural component, plays an important role in load distribution and provides the structure with the necessary rigidity [9, 24]. The slab system used can have a significant impact on a building's seismic behavior, modifying its overall mass, stiffness, and intrinsic vibrational frequencies [10, 25]. Slab systems, which range from flat and solid to waffle shapes, each have their own set of advantages and drawbacks, particularly when examined through the lens of architectural flexibility, structural efficacy, and serviceability [11, 26]. In seismically active areas, the importance of carefully selecting the most appropriate and efficient slab system is emphasized [12, 27]. Beyond simply conforming to the architectural and functional requirements of the structure, the slab system must be improved to enhance seismic resistance [13]. This delicate balancing act necessitates a harmonic blend of attractive design, structural robustness, and strict adherence to local building and seismic standards [14].

Developments in structural engineering and material sciences have brought in a variety of improved slab systems and building approaches, many of which promise increased seismic resistance [15]. Base isolation techniques, for example, which are based on the principle of disconnecting the structure from the ground, can significantly reduce the seismic forces transferred to the structure [16]. Concurrently, energy dissipation devices can effectively harness and diffuse seismic energy, reducing strains on the structure [3]. To summarize, as our urban environments become increasingly congested with skyscrapers, the importance of seismic analysis and design in high-rise buildings grows [18]. Safeguarding these structures during seismic disturbances is a societal obligation, not only a technical challenge. The careful selection of a slab system designed for seismic zones is critical in this endeavor, ensuring that cities and their inhabitants are protected from earthquakes.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE CURRENT WORK

- Assess and compare the seismic performance of three different slab systems: flat slab, solid slab, and hollow block slab.
- Investigate the effects of seismic loads for high-rise buildings using the parameters of bending moment, story shear force, drift, base shear, displacement, deflection, and punching shear.
- Examine the short- and long-term deflections caused by seismic stresses in these slab systems, as well as the material properties in tall structures.
- Determine the most suitable slab system for tall structures in seismic zones, taking safety and construction feasibility into account.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Structural Model Analysis

For comparison, three slab systems were considered: flat, solid, and hollow block slab. For assessing the seismic performance, structural models for each of the slab types have been constructed using modal analysis techniques. Important

characteristics such as base shear, story shear force, bending moment, story drift, story deflection, and punching shear have been determined using the structural analysis approach.

B. Result Comparison

In the comparison of the structural analysis results for the three slab systems, parameters such as construction cost, seismic performance, and building time were investigated. The primary objective of this research was to find the best slab system for high structures in seismically active areas.

C. Sensitivity Analysis

To examine and assess the impact of different design features on the seismic performance of each type of slab, a study was conducted. The investigation attempted to identify the important design characteristics that have a substantial impact on the seismic performance of slab structures.

D. Result Validation

To assess the accuracy of the structural analysis results, a comparison was made between the seismic performance for each type of slab and the results from the literature review. This enabled an evaluation of the output's consistency and dependability.

E. Conclusion

The most acceptable slab option for high-rise buildings in seismically prone areas was established through comparative and sensitivity research. The seismic performance of the various slab systems was taken into consideration as a part of the decision. This choice is intended to provide the most effective slab construction for more effective earthquake resilience in such locations.

IV. BUILDING SPECIFICATIONS

TABLE I. SPECIFICATIONS OF REINFORCED CONCRETE SLAB SYSTEMS

Specifications	Slab system type		
	Flat	Solid	Hollow block
Total number of storeys	7	7	7
Height of a typical floor (m)	3	3	3
Height of the first floor (m)	4	4	4
Total depth of slab (cm)	22	12	28
Maximum span length (m)	3.6	3.6	3.6
Cross-section of beams (cm ²)	50×30	50×30	50×30
Cross-sections of columns (cm ²)	(60, 80, 90, 100, 110)×30		
Size of ribs (cm)	-	-	15
Spacing of ribs (cm)	-	-	55
Compressive strength of concrete (Mpa)	24	24	24
Longitudinal steel rebar	Fy420	Fy420	Fy420
Lateral steel rebar	Fy240	Fy240	Fy240

V. BUILDING DESIGN LOADS

The multi-story building was designed in accordance with the Saudi building codes for concrete structures. The loads were defined in accordance with SBC 301 for live and dead loads for the specific application and occupancy. The seismic loads were defined using the Static Equivalent Method (SEM) and the Response Spectrum Method (RSE) in accordance with SBC 304C.

A. Dead Loads

- Self-weight of concrete with a density of 24 kN/m³.
- Superimposed deadloads for the residential and commercial occupancy of 2 kN/m².
- Superimposed load of the helicopter pad of 1.2 kN/m².

B. Live Loads

- Service live load of floor slabs of 3 kN/m².
- Service live load of staircases of 5 kN/m².
- Helicopter landing and take-off load of 2.87 kN/m².

C. Seismic Loads

- Spectral response acceleration, SDS = 0.254
- Spectral response acceleration, SD1 = 0.073
- Transition period = 4
- Site class: B
- Seismic occupancy importance factor, I = 1.25
- Response modification factor(s), R = 4
- System overstrength factor = 2.5

VI. STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS MODELS

Fig. 1. ETABS Software Model: (a)-(b) Flat, (c)-(d) solid, (e)-(f) hollow block slab.

VII. SLABS STRUCTURAL RESPONSE COMPARISON

A. Story Displacement Comparison

Among the three slab systems, the flat slab has the greatest x-direction story displacement, with a maximum displacement

in story 7 of 2.334 mm. In the solid slab system, the least amount of displacement of 2.164 mm is found in story 7, as illustrated in Figure 2. The hollow block slab has the maximum story displacement in the y-direction of 1.776 mm in story 7. The least displacement is found to be 1.707 mm in story 7 for the solid slab system.

TABLE II. SPECIFICATIONS OF REINFORCED CONCRETE SLAB SYSTEMS

Story Unit	Flat Slab		Solid slab		Hollow block slab	
	mm		mm		mm	
Direction	x	y	x	y	x	y
7	2.334	1.741	2.164	1.707	2.207	1.776
6	2.058	1.565	1.906	1.535	1.967	1.603
5	1.754	1.365	1.623	1.339	1.697	1.406
4	1.427	1.141	1.317	1.117	1.399	1.183
3	1.085	0.898	0.998	0.876	1.080	0.940
2	0.743	0.648	0.681	0.628	0.755	0.687
1	0.42	0.407	0.384	0.390	0.440	0.439

Fig. 2. Maximum story displacement in (a) x and (b) y direction.

B. Base Shear Reactions Comparison

The hollow block slab has the highest base shear reactions according to the RSE analysis, with 712.33 kN in the x- and 921.26 kN in the y-direction. As demonstrated in Figure 3, the solid slab system has the lowest base shear values of 623.72 kN and 799.91 kN in the x- and y-direction, respectively.

C. Story Drift Comparison

The flat slab system exhibits the maximum story drift in the X-direction due to the response spectrum, with a ratio of 0.000114 between stories 3 and 4, as shown in Figure 4.

TABLE III. BASE SHEAR COMPARISON FOR RESPONSE SPECTRUM

Unit	kN	
Direction	x	y
Flat	641.055	839.706
Solid	623.719	799.906
Hollow block	712.331	921.262

Fig. 3. Base shear comparison of slab types.

TABLE IV. MAXIMUM STORY DRIFTS FOR RESPONSE SPECTRUM IN THE X-DIRECTION

Slab type	Flat	Solid	Hollow block
Unit	mm/mm	mm/mm	mm/mm
Story	x - direction		
7	0.000092	0.000086	0.000073
6	0.000102	0.000095	0.000082
5	0.00011	0.000102	0.000091
4	0.000114	0.000107	0.000097
3	0.000114	0.000106	0.000099
2	0.000108	0.0001	0.000096
1	0.000085	0.000078	0.00008

Fig. 4. Maximum story drifts in the x - direction.

Because of the geometry of the multistory building, the values of story drifts in the y-direction are nearly the same for all types of slabs, as illustrated in Figure 5.

D. Maximum Column Forces

Maximum column force reactions are evaluated in relation to the maximum applied design loads on reinforced concrete columns at the bottom of each column for each floor. Column C32 was chosen because it has the highest resultant force values of any slab type. It has a tributary area of 0.64 m² and stretches from story 1 to story 7. The hollow block slab had the highest axial load at 1239.65 kN in story 6, whereas the solid slab had the lowest at 725.16 kN in level 5. In story 1, the hollow block slab has the highest shear force of 1278.1 kN, whereas the solid slab has the lowest shear force of 1077.57 kN in story 1 as shown in Table VI.

TABLE V. MAXIMUM STORY DRIFTS FOR RESPONSE SPECTRUM IN THE X-DIRECTION

Slab type	Flat	Solid	Hollow block
Unit	mm/mm	mm/mm	mm/mm
Story	x - direction		
7	0.000061	0.000059	0.000058
6	0.000069	0.000068	0.000066
5	0.000077	0.000076	0.000075
4	0.000083	0.000083	0.000081
3	0.000085	0.000085	0.000085
2	0.000083	0.000082	0.000083
1	0.00007	0.000067	0.000072

Fig. 5. Maximum story drifts in the y - direction.

E. Maximum Bending Moment

At the bottom of each column, the maximum bending moment reactions are calculated. For all slab types, one column with the greatest resulting bending moment was chosen. As indicated in Table VII, the maximum bending moment resultant value is found in the Hollow Block slab at 3116.21 kN-m in story 1, while the lowest value is found in the Solid slab at 2630.64 kN-m in story 1.

TABLE VI. COLUMN MAXIMUM DESIGN FORCES

Slab type	Flat			Solid			Hollow block		
	P	V2	V3	P	V2	V3	P	V2	V3
Unit	kN	kN	kN	kN	kN	kN	kN	kN	kN
Story 7	-797.32	27.71	-50.69	578.42	-98.08	-7.89	964.00	-70.10	263.42
Story 6	-929.53	-22.84	-338.78	697.34	13.91	347.09	1239.66	15.60	415.52
Story 5	-900.26	-57.67	207.20	725.16	104.63	-88.25	1212.96	77.28	-250.12
Story 4	-676.19	-16.25	613.24	547.07	66.88	-518.17	789.00	37.14	-765.33
Story 3	-403.65	31.93	471.59	258.67	-20.06	-477.52	243.00	-31.42	-601.25
Story 2	-291.74	29.56	28.30	108.58	-55.33	-51.37	9.21	-42.11	12.39
Story 1	-429.41	-25.48	-1239.70	255.21	0.77	1077.57	290.56	18.31	1278.10

TABLE VII. COLUMN MAXIMUM DESIGN MOMENTS

Slab type	Flat		Solid		Hollow block	
	M2	M3	M2	M3	M2	M3
	(kN-m)					
7	-716.42	76.92	442.08	-181.45	883.31	-124.14
6	-1439.98	-7.70	1149.57	-10.89	1495.66	7.38
5	-813.73	-83.36	777.12	148.77	697.55	112.89
4	667.95	-44.28	-467.03	119.29	-887.78	66.90
3	1622.07	33.43	-1385.84	-11.50	-1750.41	-38.04
2	1536.32	52.03	-1315.40	-85.55	-1363.79	-67.10
1	-3115.16	-50.78	2630.64	-0.03	3116.21	38.13

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

Previous research has explored the effects of seismic loads on several concrete slab systems, such as the flat slab system, the solid slab system, and the hollow block slab system, with the aim of better understanding the reaction of multistory building designs that use these diverse slab systems. In comparison to previous research findings, the current study considered several critical Saudi building code factors, including story displacement, story drift, column force, base shear, and bending moments. The solid slab system demonstrated the least displacement, being 7.3% less than that of the flat slab method. Furthermore, the solid slab system displayed 13.2% less base shear than the hollow block slab system.

In addition, compared to the hollow block slab system, the solid slab system displayed the lowest axial column forces, with a 42% reduction. When compared to the hollow block slab system, it had the lowest bending moments, with a 16% reduction. The hollow block slab system showed the lowest story drift, with a 15% reduction when compared to the flat slab system. Despite these findings, it is critical to recognize the study's limitations. The study was limited to Saudi construction restrictions and did not account for possible changes in seismic conditions between locations.

IX. POSSIBLE FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

Considering the current results and the constantly evolving discipline of structural engineering, the following areas identify as promising for future research:

- **Long-Term Durability and Effects:** A more comprehensive investigation of the long-term resilience of various slab systems is necessary. This requires assessing their durability, especially when subjected to frequent seismic disturbances over a long period of time.
- **Analysis of Dynamic Response:** A thorough investigation into the dynamic properties of these structural systems is required. Understanding their nonlinear responses under a range of earthquake conditions could reveal insight into their adaptability and robustness.
- **Construction Material Innovations:** With the rapid technical advances in construction materials, there is an exciting opportunity to investigate the integration of innovative materials or hybrid systems. Such research could

potentially reveal construction approaches that considerably improve structural seismic performance.

These directions not only correspond to the current research environment, but, also aim to address some of the most pressing difficulties in seismic engineering.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. D. Imran, P. Scholar, and M. M. Ahmed, "Dynamic Analysis of G+20 Residential Building in Zone-2 and Zone-5 by Using Etabs," *International Research Journal in Advanced Engineering and Technology*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 2680–2684, Jan. 2018.
- [2] H. S. Mohana and M. R. Kavan, "Comparative Study of Flat Slab and Conventional Slab Structure Using ETABS for Different Earthquake Zones of India," *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 1931–1936, Jun. 2015.
- [3] R. Azad and S. Setia, "Response of Different RC Slab Systems in Buildings to Seismic Excitations," in *Sustainable Development in Civil and Electrical Engineering*, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/1236/1/012004>.
- [4] I. Sococol, P. Mihai, T.-C. Petrescu, F. Nedeff, V. Nedeff, and M. Agop, "Analytical Study Regarding the Seismic Response of a Moment-Resisting (MR) Reinforced Concrete (RC) Frame System with Reduced Cross Sections of the RC Beams," *Buildings*, vol. 12, no. 7, Jul. 2022, Art. no. 983, <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings12070983>.
- [5] M. Betti, L. Galano, and A. Vignoli, "Comparative analysis on the seismic behaviour of unreinforced masonry buildings with flexible diaphragms," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 61, pp. 195–208, Mar. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2013.12.038>.
- [6] R. A. Hakim, M. S. A. Alama, and S. A. Ashour, "Seismic Assessment of an RC Building Using Pushover Analysis," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 631–635, Jun. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.428>.
- [7] H. I. Polat, "Analysis of a Frame-Shear Wall Concrete Structure by Using Base Isolation and Evaluation of Structure-Soil Interaction," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 2282–2287, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1611>.
- [8] M. Bakale and V. T.S., "Seismic behavior of multi-story structure with different types of slabs," *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 507–517, Jan. 2017.
- [9] M. S. Latha and K. Pratibha, "Analysis and comparison of conventional slab and grid slab for symmetric and asymmetric structures," *Materials Today: Proceedings*, vol. 46, pp. 1860–1869, Jan. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2020.12.1245>.
- [10] D. D. Nguyen and C. N. Nguyen, "Seismic Responses of NPP Structures Considering the Effects of Lead Rubber Bearing," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 6500–6503, Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3926>.
- [11] O. Badla, "Seismic Assessment of Steel Frames Subjected to Multi-hazards," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 9565–9569, Dec. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5311>.
- [12] C. H. L. Nishanth, Y. Sai Swaroop, D. C. K. Jagarapu, and P. Kumar Jogi, "Analysis and design of commercial building with different slab arrangements using ETABS," *Materials Today: Proceedings*, vol. 33, pp. 700–704, Jan. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2020.05.823>.
- [13] A. Zakaria, M. S. R. Krishna, and S. V. Surendhar, "Comparative Study of the Seismic Performance of Rcc Building with Ribbed Slab and Grid Slab," *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 139–144, 2019.
- [14] P. Singh and R. Joshi, "Seismic Analysis of High Rise Building Structure Considering Flat and Grid Slab: A Review," *International Journal of Scientific Research in Civil Engineering*, vol. 3, no. 5, pp. 8–13, Sep. 2019.
- [15] R. P. Apostolska, G. S. Necevska-Cvetanovska, J. P. Cvetanovska, and N. Mircic, "Seismic Performance of Flat-Slab Building Structural Systems," in *The 14 th World Conference on Earthquake Engineering*, Beijing, China, Oct. 2008.

- [16] T. Öztürk and Z. Öztürk, "The Effects of the Type of Slab on Structural System in the Multi-Storey Reinforced Concrete Buildings," in *The 14th World Conference on Earthquake Engineering*, Beijing, China, Oct. 2008.
- [17] S. Borkar, K. Dabhekar, I. Khedekar, and S. Jaju, "Analysis of Flat Slab Structures in Comparison with Conventional Slab Structures," in *International Conference on Contemporary and Sustainable Infrastructure*, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/822/1/012049>.
- [18] S. B. Asl, H. S. Naeini, L. S. Ensaniat, R. Khorshidian, S. Alipour, and S. B. Asl, "Injury Prevention among Construction Workers: A Case Study on Iranian Steel Bar Bending Workers," *International Journal of Medical, Health, Biomedical, Bioengineering and Pharmaceutical Engineering*, vol. 8, no. 8, pp. 458–461, 2014.
- [19] S. Nazari Enjedani and M. Khanal, "Development of a Turning Movement Estimator Using CV Data," *Future Transportation*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 349–367, Mar. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.3390/futuretransp3010021>.
- [20] S. Irají, R. Soltanmohammadi, E. R. Munoz, A. Winter, R. V. de Almeida, and A. C. Vidal, "Experimental Investigation of Waterflooding Performance by Increasing Copper Ions in Brazilian Pre-Salt Rock," in *83rd EAGE Annual Conference & Exhibition*, Jun. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.3997/2214-4609.202210500>.
- [21] E. Jafarzadeh, A. Kabiri-Samani, B. Boroomand, and A. Bohluly, "Analytical modeling of flexible circular submerged mound motion in gravity waves," *Journal of Ocean Engineering and Marine Energy*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 181–190, Feb. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40722-022-00248-9>.
- [22] N. Shakouri Mahmoudabadi, "The Use Of Viscous Dampers For Retrofitting Of Reinforced Concrete Frames," *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education*, vol. 12, no. 13, pp. 7739–7744, Feb. 2021.
- [23] E. Jafarzadeh, A. Bohluly, A. Kabiri-Samani, and S. Mansourzadeh, "A study on the performance of circular and rectangular submerged breakwaters using non-uniform FGV method," *Coastal Engineering Journal*, vol. 65, no. 2, pp. 234–255, Apr. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1080/21664250.2023.2170688>.
- [24] L. C. Murdoch *et al.*, "Using the Shallow Strain Tensor to Characterize Deep Geologic Reservoirs," *Water Resources Research*, vol. 59, no. 2, 2023, Art. no. e2022WR032920, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022WR032920>.
- [25] L. C. Murdoch, L. N. Germanovich, S. Roudini, S. J. DeWolf, L. Hua, and R. W. Moak, "A Type-Curve Approach for Evaluating Aquifer Properties by Interpreting Shallow Strain Measured During Well Tests," *Water Resources Research*, vol. 57, no. 9, 2021, Art. no. e2021WR029613, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021WR029613>.
- [26] P. Alipour, *The BEM and DRBEM schemes for the numerical solution of the two-dimensional time-fractional diffusion-wave equations*. 2023.

Development of Renewable Energy Sources to Serve Agriculture in Vietnam: A Strategic Assessment using the SWOT Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Agriculture plays an important role in the economy of many countries, including Vietnam. Traditional agricultural manufacturing processes are inefficient in energy and material consumption and generate substantial carbon emissions. In recent decades, environmentalists and policymakers have been actively involved in the transition from conventional fossil fuels to renewables. This study investigated the potential Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats (SWOT) associated with developing Renewable Energy sources to serve agriculture in Vietnam. The results of the analysis revealed that renewable energy sources have numerous strengths, including reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and the cost of electricity, accessing new technologies, and providing economic benefits to farmers. However, the system also faces several weaknesses and threats, such as policy mechanisms, infrastructure, investment capital, foreign-dependent technologies, and potential environmental impacts. This study provides strategic recommendations to maximize the potential of agrivoltaic systems while mitigating their weaknesses and threats. The findings can help stakeholders make informed decisions and take appropriate actions in the development of renewable energy sources in agriculture.

Keywords-renewable energy; agricultural energy; internet of things; smart agriculture; SWOT analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

Agriculture plays an important role in the economy of many countries, including Vietnam. Agricultural activities require direct and indirect energy consumption to perform daily operating processes, such as irrigation, lighting, heating, cooling, and drying. The use of traditional energy sources has caused serious environmental problems, as the increase in mechanized activities in agriculture increases the use of fossil

fuels [1]. The use of fossil fuels in agriculture causes high carbon emissions that lead to global warming. In such a context, the conversion of energy from one form to another is very necessary to run a process. Renewable energy sources are potential solutions to reduce environmental effects and meet current agricultural energy demands.

Several countries have launched strategies to develop renewable energy sources and provide clean energy sources for

agriculture. For example, China is planning to implement photovoltaic systems in rural areas to avoid the use of fossil fuels using incentive policies regarding financial subsidies and taxation [2]. In general, this energy policy is important in optimally adapting energy management initiatives, adopting energy saving to reduce carbon emissions, and applying green technology to improve energy efficiency. However, such policies have advantages and disadvantages for the development and application of renewable energy sources for agricultural production. In Vietnam, renewable energy production sources, such as the sun, water, wind, and biomass, can help achieve the energy production goal cleanly and sustainably for the power consumption of different sectors, such as agriculture. Replacing conventional energy with low-carbon renewable electricity is one of the easiest ways to reduce emissions. As an integral part of energy policy, governments enact renewable energy policies to achieve a more rapid transition to sustainable energy. The Vietnamese Government considers energy-related policies a major concern, since unexpected economic, social, and environmental impacts may severely affect the country's economy and its people [3]. In [4], a green scenario was proposed for electricity generation in Vietnam by 2030. Vietnam needs to have access to secure energy supplies and sustainably shift its energy resources from fossil fuels to renewable energy sources. However, Vietnam has not been able to make the best use of its renewable energy potential and development policies for agricultural production activities.

This paper adopted an integrated Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats (SWOT) analysis to evaluate strategies for the development of agricultural energy systems in Vietnam. This study not only identifies key factors that affect the Vietnamese agricultural energy sector but can also serve as a guide for various energy stakeholders and policy-makers to better understand the challenges and opportunities of the agricultural energy sector and prioritize key strategies for the development of renewable energy systems in agriculture in Vietnam. Moreover, since the adoption of technology in Vietnam's agriculture is much slower than in any other developing country, a detailed SWOT analysis will be helpful. The results of the analysis are an important guide to designing long-term strategies and plans.

II. METHODOLOGY

This study used the SWOT analysis decision-making methodology to investigate strategies for the development of renewable energy sources for agriculture in Vietnam and evaluate their structural relationships. SWOT analysis is a well-known model in the business analysis of the enterprise [5]. A SWOT analysis is a well-structured strategic plan to assess the current status of the business in the market by evaluating strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats [6]. Strengths are one of the key categories that highlight the positive effects of the scenario compared to others. Weaknesses are negative factors that lead to unfavorable scenarios. Opportunities are external influences that can positively affect the scenario in the future. External factors that could reduce performance and lead to insecurities are captured under threats [7]. The findings of a SWOT analysis help companies build on their strengths, realize

new opportunities, and work toward minimization or elimination of any possible threat [8]. Figure 1 shows the step-by-step procedure of SWOT analysis.

Fig. 1. SWOT analysis framework.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2 presents the framework and a summary of the evaluation in quadrant form of the 24 factors identified by the SWOT analysis.

A. Strengths

The Vietnamese government cares about the development of clean energy and smart agriculture. Agriculture received the close attention of the State in the energy transition process of the country. Vietnam has prioritized the investment and use of renewable energy and has encouraged organizations and individuals to participate in its development and use in all production areas, including agriculture. In 2007, the Vietnamese government formulated the national energy development strategy up to 2020 with a vision for 2050 [9]. To meet these growing energy demands and ensure energy security, the government has taken various initiatives to diversify energy sources, including renewable energy sources. For instance, Vietnam's 2030 renewable energy development strategy, with a vision for 2050, was approved in 2015. Under this decision, the total electricity generation from renewable sources is expected to reach 101, 186, and 452 billion kWh in 2020, 2030, and 2050, respectively, compared to 58 billion kWh in 2015 [10]. In this context, in early 2020, the government developed and issued a strategic national energy development orientation for 2030, with a vision for 2045, with revised guidelines for the energy sector [11]. In May 2023, the Power Development Plan (PDP8) was approved, reflecting the results of numerous drafts and revisions for nearly three years [12].

1) Potential for Renewable Energy Sources

Vietnam has a diverse range of renewable energy resources, including biomass, solar, wind, hydroelectricity, and geothermal. Vietnam has a high solar energy potential, ranging from 4 to 5 kWh/m² daily average for the entire country, while

the average sunshine hours range from 1600 to 2600 h in a year [13-15]. The average annual sunshine hours are 1500-1700 h in the northern part, while in central and southern Vietnam they are 2000-2600 h. Solar power in Vietnam developed very quickly in the period 2019-2021 and was ranked 10th on the list of countries having the largest solar power capacity with a total installed solar power capacity of 17.4 GW [16]. Compared to all renewable energy sources, solar energy has the greatest potential. For wind energy, Vietnam has the largest wind potential in Southeast Asia, as its total wind power potential is approximately 513,360 MW, with more than 8% of Vietnam's area having a very promising wind power potential [17-18]. More than 39% of Vietnam's area has an average annual wind speed of more than 6 m/s at an altitude of 65 m, and more than

8% of Vietnam's area has an average annual wind speed of more than 7 m/s, corresponding to a wind resource potential of 512 and 110 GW.

2) Rapid Development in Information Technology

A digital revolution has been spreading through all parts of the economy and society in the past few decades due to the rapid development of information and communication technologies [19]. In recent years, Vietnam has developed strongly in information technology to meet the needs of society. The Government promulgated the National Strategy on the development of the digital economy and digital society to 2025, with a vision to 2030, including the application of information technology in agriculture and energy [20].

Fig. 2. Summary of the SWOT analysis for the development of an agricultural energy IoT system in Vietnam.

B. Weaknesses

1) Dependence on External Factors

The natural energy sources are highly dependent on weather conditions, terrain, climate, etc. In bad weather conditions, renewable energy technologies, such as photovoltaics or wind turbine generators, will be used less often. Wind speed variations alter the power generated through wind turbines, whereas the power produced through photovoltaics is affected by deviations in solar radiation and varying temperatures [21]. Therefore, weather conditions affect the stability, reliability, and quality of the power supplied to agricultural production. In addition, renewable energy systems respond rapidly to grid disturbances and increase the instability of the grid due to the fast response characteristics of power electronics [22].

2) Lack of Infrastructure Investment

Infrastructure plays an important role in an agricultural energy Internet of Things (IoT) system, as it includes broadband telecommunication networks (optical cables and

new generation mobile network infrastructures), information technology, electricity grid, digital technology equipment, construction of main roads, IoT connections, and other essential infrastructure works related to renewable energy projects and hi-tech agriculture. The technical infrastructure for renewable energy exploitation has not yet developed, showing that investors must spend a large amount of capital to invest in initial infrastructure (roads, electricity, water lines, etc.). Furthermore, in rural areas, many establishments providing telecommunications services and Internet access are still weak, the means of information transmission are relatively outdated, and the covered areas are very limited.

3) Foreign Dependent Technologies

The technologies needed are mostly imported and depend on foreign suppliers, while the customization, adjustment, and mastery of the technology are very limited. In addition, technologies depend greatly on international prices and the prevailing policies of partners. Therefore, more support is needed from international organizations and governments related to technology transfer and financial and human support.

4) *High Initial Cost of Agricultural Energy Projects*

The exploitation of renewable energy resources in Vietnam has a high cost compared to traditional energy sources. The cost of installing, building, monitoring software, maintenance, and equipment for high-tech agricultural farm models is expensive compared to fossil fuels. It is difficult to attract investors to this sector, especially in countries that have some risks [23]. Several studies claimed that renewable energy projects are competitive with fossil fuel technologies based on their Levelized Costs Of Electricity (LCOE), the most common indicator to compare the cost competitiveness of electricity generation technologies [24].

5) *Lack of Technically Qualified Personnel*

The agricultural production and labor forces cannot meet the requirements for applying novel technologies in agriculture. Especially in regions with underdeveloped economies [25].

6) *Lack of Standardization in the Synchronous Connection*

The installation of renewable energy power systems in some construction projects and farms is not guaranteed. Furthermore, the capacity to implement solutions and investment projects is still limited. The deployment and installation of rooftop solar power systems at livestock and cropping farms have not met the regulations on farm economic criteria, planning, and land use plans. There is also a lack of standardization in synchronous connections between data transmitters and a difficulty in integration and IoT communication between devices from different manufacturers.

C. *Opportunities*

1) *Government Incentives*

Governments offer incentives to promote the use of renewable energy in agriculture, including grants, tax credits, and subsidies. In 2017, a very generous Feed-In Tariff (FIT) rate was introduced, approximately 10.5% higher than the average retail tariff, through a combination of net metering and a FIT-type scheme of 2086 VND/kWh or 0.0935 US\$/kWh [26]. In April 2020, the government announced reduced FITs of 83.8 US\$/MWh for new rooftop solar projects, 70.9 US\$/MWh for new ground-mounted solar photovoltaics, and 76.9 US\$/MWh for new floating solar projects [27].

2) *Contribution to Greenhouse Gas Emission Reduction*

Agriculture is one of the key drivers of environmental deterioration, linked to GHG emissions and labeled as ultrasensitive to climate change. Many recent studies have shown that renewable energy contributes to environmental sustainability and reduces GHGs through the transition from fossil fuels. The transition from fossil energy to renewable energy can achieve a win-win situation by resolving the trade-off between environment, poverty, and energy poverty [28]. Several studies considered the relationship between Research and Development (R&D) and GHGs. R&D investment in renewable technologies has a significant positive effect on environmental quality by reducing a variety of pollutants, including carbon dioxide, methane, and other pollutants [29]. To overcome these limitations, recommendations on

sustainable and climate-smart agriculture would improve productivity and resilience while reducing emissions [30].

3) *Connecting Businesses and Investors*

Creating favorable conditions to connect businesses and investors in the fields of renewable energy and high-tech agriculture can lead to knowledge exchange and system operation experiences.

4) *Reducing the Cost of Electricity in Agricultural Production*

Modern agriculture requires a much greater energy input than conventional agriculture. Solar energy can be used in agriculture in numerous ways, resulting in reduction in electricity costs, increased independence, and reduced emissions. Solar energy applications in agriculture are on the rise for irrigation, lighting, heating, cooling, and drying. For example, 100% renewable energy is becoming technically feasible and economically viable with decreasing costs every year [31]. Solar heat inside a greenhouse can be stored for later use using a heat storage material/phase and reduce heating costs [32].

5) *Accessing New Technologies in Agricultural Production*

Farmers have the opportunity to access new technologies in agricultural production to improve crop production and the quality of agricultural products, such as IoT technology with accurate data collection sensors on climate, growing conditions, and the health of plants or animals, and intelligent automation technology with robots and machinery in farming activities [33]. Smart agriculture that incorporates advanced Internet-based information technology can help in the intelligent management of agricultural production [34-35]. With an improved design, farmers can easily understand how to self-integrate, self-troubleshoot, and self-maintain the IoT environmental monitoring system without requiring expertise on the farm site. As a result, it can increase farmers' willingness to accept innovative technologies and help them gain control over growing crops. In the end, such technologies will allow them to run more predictable, efficient, and profitable agribusiness [36].

6) *Contributing to the Promotion of Local Economy and Social Development*

The road system serves the construction of the rural transport system. Renewable energy projects and high-tech agriculture also contribute to multitarget economic development and increase budget revenue for localities, as they help create jobs, increase income for farmers, contribute to economic restructuring, increase the value of industrial production, and promote social and economic development.

7) *Increasing Profitability for Farmers and Businesses*

Smart agriculture can create opportunities for entrepreneurs, investors, scientists, and farmers to research and develop digital transformation and digital technology applications in agriculture, support automated and optimized production processes, and help farmers increase productivity and reduce production costs.

D. Threats

1) Policy Mechanisms

Although Vietnam has great potential for renewable energy sources (wind, solar), the number of projects implemented is still very small due to the lack of strong enough and synchronous policies, including regulations to investigate and evaluate the potential for their exploitation and use. The oversimplification of the FIT price mechanism issued by the government has led to uneven development of solar power systems, as most grid-connected solar power systems are concentrated in the central and southern regions [37]. Institutional barriers, such as market-controlled mechanisms and unstable supporting policies, also limit investment in renewable power sectors. As a result, although energy policies and plans are being established towards cleaner energy production, progress is slow. However, Vietnam faces other challenges when it comes to solar energy, which cannot be simply addressed by providing financial incentives. High population density, land morphology, and geography make land allocation for renewable energy, particularly solar farms, quite challenging [38].

2) Investment Capital and the Ability to Arrange Capital for Investors

The demand for energy in agriculture is increasing day by day. Investors are moving towards the development of renewable energy sources for agricultural production purposes, making renewable energy more competitive, leading to a high level of capital investment in renewable energy projects. Wind power production costs have become more competitive due to the rapid development of technologies and the reduction of installation costs. The capital costs of a wind power project can be listed as follows: turbine cost, civil works (including construction costs for site preparation and foundations for the towers), grid connection costs (including transformers and connections to local distribution), project planning costs, and others such as road construction, building, and control systems [39]. In addition, high-tech agriculture requires a huge capital investment. A high-tech agricultural project can require much more investment than traditional methods, such as initial costs for infrastructure investment, design consultancy, operation and maintenance of renewable energy systems, and design and development of the equipment for monitoring and controlling smart agricultural farm models.

3) Lack of Awareness and Technology Know-How

The human resources qualifications of training institutions that specialize in the operation, maintenance, and repair of electrical equipment related to renewable energy have not yet developed strongly, leading to low labor productivity in some areas. This leads to a lack of awareness and know-how of renewable energy technologies, IoT technology, control automation equipment, and smart electronic equipment in high-tech agricultural models. Many areas lack Internet access, creating many challenges in applying technology and deploying IoT applications to automate production. Human resources in the agricultural sector are currently not trained in technological and technical advances. Although labor in rural areas is abundant, industrial discipline is not high and requires

a lot of training time. Farmers are still familiar with traditional methods, do not use technology proficiently, and have limited discipline in organizing production, complying with processes, using chemicals, and caring for short-term profits.

4) Technology and Technique

Exploiting, accessing, and using renewable energy technologies and smart electronic devices depends on technology transfer from foreign countries. There are also difficulties in controlling and regulating the power system when the proportion of renewable energy sources in the system increases, due to unstable power generation and weather dependence. The sudden increase in this type of energy source causes many problems in the operation of the power system, such as full load, local overload, and a decrease in system inertia. With increasing penetration of renewable energy, the frequency stability of the system will gradually deteriorate [40]. In addition, there is a lack of capacity to manage, operate, maintain, and repair renewable energy equipment, a lack of software expertise, a lack of assessment information on the potential of renewable energy sources, and the ability to connect renewable energy projects to the grid after completion. Domestic contractors do not have much experience in the construction and utilization of new technology and complicated techniques.

5) Effects of Climate Change

Renewable energy sources primarily depend on climatic conditions. The intermittency and randomness of renewable energy affect the operation of the power system. Wind power has the characteristics of being completely dependent on weather and climate, uncontrollable, fluctuating with a large amplitude within the range of installed capacity, and generating very different amounts of electricity from month to month and year to year. As solar power is only generated during the day, skyrockets at noon and then rapidly decreases, it is unable to cover the demands during the peak hours in the evening.

6) Indirect Pollution

The production and use of renewable energy sources can pose environmental risks, such as pollution and habitat destruction, which must be carefully managed. Although photovoltaic power generation technology is more environmentally friendly than traditional energy industries and can achieve zero CO₂ emissions during the operation phase, the waste generated during the production process and after the end of life harms the environment and cannot be ignored [41]. The waste of old solar panels poses a global environmental problem. The disposal of solar panels, which include lead, chromium, and cadmium, is prevalent, but little is done to mitigate its detrimental impact [42].

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Conclusion

Developing intelligent agricultural systems in general and in agriculture is a key goal of Vietnam. SWOT analysis provided some strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats in the development of renewable energy sources to serve agriculture in Vietnam, and strategic recommendations

were provided to maximize their potential. However, the system has several weaknesses, including its lack of infrastructure investment, high initial cost, and the lack of technically qualified personnel. The adoption of renewable energy sources to serve agriculture may face challenges in areas with limited policy mechanisms, inadequate technical capacity, low investment capital, and a lack of technically qualified personnel. Despite these weaknesses, the analysis identified several opportunities for the development of renewable energy sources to serve agriculture, including government incentives, connecting businesses and investors, and access to new technologies in agricultural production. To maximize the potential of renewable energy sources, several strategic recommendations were provided, such as increasing public awareness and support, developing innovative financing mechanisms, and conducting further research to address potential negative impacts. This analysis demonstrated that renewable energy sources have the potential to provide a sustainable solution for both energy and food production. However, to fully realize this potential, policymakers, farmers, and energy companies must work together to address the challenges and opportunities presented. However, the future looks bright for the development of renewable energy sources to serve agriculture, which are both technically and commercially feasible.

B. Recommendations

Renewable energy sources are the best option for rural areas, as they not only contribute to the development of intelligent agriculture systems but also provide benefits, such as sustainability, decreased GHG emissions, improvement in social structure, and local development, in addition to other trivial benefits. The results of this study lead to the following recommendations to decision-makers to help in the development of agricultural renewable energy IoT systems:

- As the cost of consulting, equipment, design, and construction of agricultural renewable energy IoT models is very high, it is necessary to have tax incentives for organizations and businesses, creating favorable conditions for farmers to develop renewable energy sources to provide electricity for agricultural production and expand the model in rural areas far from the center.
- Creating a favorable legal framework for investors in rural energy projects.
- Developing standards for the development of renewable energy sources for agricultural and rural farm models.
- The government should offer incentives, including low-interest financing for businesses and farmers, to stimulate growth and expand the use of renewable energy sources for agricultural models.
- Build centers for effective research, reception, and application of technical advances and new technologies in production and technology transfer in the field of renewable energy and high-tech agriculture for the development of current and future projects.
- Provide education and training to the rural population on the maintenance of renewable energy sources.
- Strengthen international cooperation to attract capital and promote technology transfer in the fields of renewable energy and high-tech agriculture.
- Encourage non-state investors to invest in smart grids to ensure efficient and economical use of electricity.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Z. Y. Zhao *et al.*, "Environmental risk of multi-year polythene film mulching and its green solution in arid irrigation region," *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, vol. 435, Aug. 2022, Art. no. 128981, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2022.128981>.
- [2] B. Lin and Z. Jiang, "Estimates of energy subsidies in China and impact of energy subsidy reform," *Energy Economics*, vol. 33, no. 2, pp. 273–283, Mar. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2010.07.005>.
- [3] D. Nong, C. Wang, and A. Q. Al-Amin, "A critical review of energy resources, policies and scientific studies towards a cleaner and more sustainable economy in Vietnam," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 134, Dec. 2020, Art. no. 110117, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2020.110117>.
- [4] V. H. M. Nguyen, L. D. L. Nguyen, C. V. Vo, and B. T. T. Phan, "Green Scenarios for Power Generation in Vietnam by 2030," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 4019–4026, Apr. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2658>.
- [5] J. W. Bull *et al.*, "Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats: A SWOT analysis of the ecosystem services framework," *Ecosystem Services*, vol. 17, pp. 99–111, Feb. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2015.11.012>.
- [6] Z. Srdjevic, R. Bajcetic, and B. Srdjevic, "Identifying the Criteria Set for Multicriteria Decision Making Based on SWOT/PESTLE Analysis: A Case Study of Reconstructing A Water Intake Structure," *Water Resources Management*, vol. 26, no. 12, pp. 3379–3393, Sep. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11269-012-0077-2>.
- [7] F. David, F. David, and M. David, *Strategic Management: A Competitive Advantage Approach, Concepts*, 16th edition. Boston, MA, USA: Pearson, 2016.
- [8] B. Phadermrod, R. M. Crowder, and G. B. Wills, "Importance-Performance Analysis based SWOT analysis," *International Journal of Information Management*, vol. 44, pp. 194–203, Feb. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2016.03.009>.
- [9] "Approving Vietnam's National Energy Development Strategy up to 2020, with Vision to 2050," Vietnam Government, Hanoi, Vietnam, Decision 1855/QĐ-TTg, 2007.
- [10] M. Melikoglu, "Vision 2023: Assessing the feasibility of electricity and biogas production from municipal solid waste in Turkey," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 19, pp. 52–63, Mar. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2012.11.017>.
- [11] "Resolution of the Politburo on Orientations of the Viet Nam's National Energy Development Strategy to 2030 and outlook to 2045," Communist Party of Vietnam, Hanoi, Vietnam, 55-NQ/TW, Feb. 2020.
- [12] "National Power Development Master Plan for the 2021-2030 period, with a vision to 2050," Government of Vietnam, Hanoi, Vietnam, Decision 500/QĐ-TTg 2023.
- [13] E. Riva Sanseverino, H. Le Thi Thuy, M.-H. Pham, M. L. Di Silvestre, N. Nguyen Quang, and S. Favuzza, "Review of Potential and Actual Penetration of Solar Power in Vietnam," *Energies*, vol. 13, no. 10, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 2529, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13102529>.

- [14] D. D. Hoat *et al.*, "Research overview of new and renewable energy in Vietnam and development orientation," *Vietnam Academy of Science and Technology*, 2007.
- [15] J. Polo *et al.*, "Solar resources and power potential mapping in Vietnam using satellite-derived and GIS-based information," *Energy Conversion and Management*, vol. 98, pp. 348–358, Jul. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2015.04.016>.
- [16] "Snapshot of Global PV Markets - 2022," International Energy Agency, IEA-PVPS T1-42:2022, Apr. 2022.
- [17] X. P. Nguyen, N. D. Le, V. V. Pham, T. T. Huynh, V. H. Dong, and A. T. Hoang, "Mission, challenges, and prospects of renewable energy development in Vietnam," *Energy Sources, Part A: Recovery, Utilization, and Environmental Effects*, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1080/15567036.2021.1965264>.
- [18] S. Roy, Y. F. Lam, M. U. Hossain, and J. C. L. Chan, "Comprehensive evaluation of electricity generation and emission reduction potential in the power sector using renewable alternatives in Vietnam," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 157, Apr. 2022, Art. no. 112009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.112009>.
- [19] C. C. Lee, Z. W. He, and F. Xiao, "How does information and communication technology affect renewable energy technology innovation? International evidence," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 200, pp. 546–557, Nov. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2022.10.015>.
- [20] "National strategy for development of digital economy and digital society to 2025 with orientation to 2030," Ministry of Information and Communications, Hanoi, Vietnam. [Online]. Available: https://mic.gov.vn/mic_2020/Pages/TinTuc/153290/Chien-luoc-quoc-gia-phan-trien-kinh-te-so-va-xa-hoi-so-den-nam-2025--dinh-huong-den-nam-2030.html.
- [21] G. Mustafa, M. H. Baloch, S. H. Qazi, S. Tahir, N. Khan, and B. A. Mirjat, "Experimental Investigation and Control of a Hybrid (PV-Wind) Energy Power System," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 6781–6786, Feb. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3964>.
- [22] Xing Zhang, Ming Li, Zixuan Guo, Jilei Wang, Feng Han, and Xinxin Fu, "Review and prospect of research on control strategy of grid-connected inverter with new energy," *Global Energy Internet*, vol. 4, no. 5, pp. 506–515, 2021.
- [23] E. B. Agyekum, V. I. Velkin, and I. Hossain, "Sustainable energy: Is it nuclear or solar for African Countries? Case study on Ghana," *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments*, vol. 37, Feb. 2020, Art. no. 100630, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seta.2020.100630>.
- [24] G. R. Timilsina, "Are renewable energy technologies cost competitive for electricity generation?," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 180, pp. 658–672, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2021.08.088>.
- [25] C. A. Vu, "Developing a high-quality workforce in the agricultural sector," *State Management Review*, vol. 3, no. 314, pp. 48–51, 2022.
- [26] E. Riva Sanseverino, H. Le Thi Thuy, M.-H. Pham, M. L. Di Silvestre, N. Nguyen Quang, and S. Favuzza, "Review of Potential and Actual Penetration of Solar Power in Vietnam," *Energies*, vol. 13, no. 10, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 2529, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13102529>.
- [27] T. N. Do *et al.*, "Vietnam's solar and wind power success: Policy implications for the other ASEAN countries," *Energy for Sustainable Development*, vol. 65, pp. 1–11, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iesd.2021.09.002>.
- [28] M. A. Baloch, Danish, S. U.-D. Khan, Z. Ş. Ulucak, and A. Ahmad, "Analyzing the relationship between poverty, income inequality, and CO₂ emission in Sub-Saharan African countries," *Science of The Total Environment*, vol. 740, Oct. 2020, Art. no. 139867, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.139867>.
- [29] A. Hailemariam, K. Ivanovski, and R. Dzhusashev, "Does R&D investment in renewable energy technologies reduce greenhouse gas emissions?," *Applied Energy*, vol. 327, Dec. 2022, Art. no. 120056, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2022.120056>.
- [30] A. Raihan *et al.*, "An econometric analysis of Greenhouse gas emissions from different agricultural factors in Bangladesh," *Energy Nexus*, vol. 9, Mar. 2023, Art. no. 100179, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nexus.2023.100179>.
- [31] "Global Energy System Based on 100% Renewable Energy - Power Sector: Chad, Niger," Lappeenranta University of Technology, Lappeenranta, Finland, 2017.
- [32] H. Mahamudul *et al.*, "Temperature Regulation of Photovoltaic Module Using Phase Change Material: A Numerical Analysis and Experimental Investigation," *International Journal of Photoenergy*, vol. 2016, Oct. 2016, Art. no. e5917028, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2016/5917028>.
- [33] K. Inoue, Y. Kaizu, S. Igarashi, and K. Imou, "The development of autonomous navigation and obstacle avoidance for a robotic mower using machine vision technique," *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, vol. 52, no. 30, pp. 173–177, Jan. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ifacol.2019.12.517>.
- [34] R. Hou, S. Li, H. Chen, G. Ren, W. Gao, and L. Liu, "Coupling mechanism and development prospect of innovative ecosystem of clean energy in smart agriculture based on blockchain," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 319, Oct. 2021, Art. no. 128466, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.128466>.
- [35] Erlangga, Y. Wihardi, and E. Nugraha, "Development Mobile Learning For Vegetable Farming In Indonesia Based On Mobile Cloud Computing," in *2020 6th International Conference on Science in Information Technology (ICSITech)*, Palu, Indonesia, Jul. 2020, pp. 6–10, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSITech49800.2020.9392074>.
- [36] N. C. Eli-Chukwu, "Applications of Artificial Intelligence in Agriculture: A Review," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 4377–4383, Aug. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2756>.
- [37] H. T. T. Le, E. R. Sanseverino, D. Q. Nguyen, M. L. Di Silvestre, S. Favuzza, and M. H. Pham, "Critical Assessment of Feed-In Tariffs and Solar Photovoltaic Development in Vietnam," *Energies*, vol. 15, no. 2, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 556, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15020556>.
- [38] H. Poursan, M. Padilha Campos Lopes, H. Ziar, D. Alves Castelo Branco, and Y. Sheng, "Evaluating floating photovoltaics (FPVs) potential in providing clean energy and supporting agricultural growth in Vietnam," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 169, Nov. 2022, Art. no. 112925, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2022.112925>.
- [39] P. A. Nguyen, M. Abbott, and T. L. T. Nguyen, "The development and cost of renewable energy resources in Vietnam," *Utilities Policy*, vol. 57, pp. 59–66, Apr. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jup.2019.01.009>.
- [40] B. Qin *et al.*, "Robust H_∞ Control of Doubly Fed Wind Generator via State-Dependent Riccati Equation Technique," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 34, no. 3, pp. 2390–2400, Feb. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRS.2018.2881687>.
- [41] L. Qi and Y. Zhang, "Effects of solar photovoltaic technology on the environment in China," *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, vol. 24, no. 28, pp. 22133–22142, Oct. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-017-9987-0>.
- [42] Ch. M. S. Kumar *et al.*, "Solar energy: A promising renewable source for meeting energy demand in Indian agriculture applications," *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments*, vol. 55, Feb. 2023, Art. no. 102905, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seta.2022.102905>.

Atmospheric CO₂ Level Measurement and Discomfort Index Calculation with the use of Low-Cost Drones

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ABSTRACT

Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) platforms are emerging as an essential tool for various studies in environmental engineering. The quadcopters drones have immense potential for sensor interfacing and stable data acquisition. These UAVs can perform critical activities like volcanic eruption monitoring, stack emission monitoring, urban air quality monitoring, identification of pollution levels in 3D space, etc. Carbon dioxide (CO₂) and the Discomfort Index (DI) are essential indicators of air quality and climate comfort. Hence, it is critical to monitor them with extreme accuracy. This study demonstrates a novel application of CO₂ profiling using low-cost drones at varied altitudes. The drone-aided vertical CO₂ profiling was carried out at 60 m AGL (Above Ground Level) during summer and winter, in Nagpur city of India. This study retrieved some exciting data on the DI. It was found that CO₂ concentration in the range of 20-70 m AGL was lower than the surface level. The derived DI was maximum at the height range of 40-50 m. Inversion was observed in the range of 30-40 m. A positive correlation between CO₂ and temperature was observed in both seasons. The lightweight commercial drones are capable of tethering sensor modules to get accurate results in less cost and effort. This type of novel tethered sensor technique could be applicable in weather forecasting, landfill surface monitoring, volcanic eruption monitoring, and other probable applications with few drone flight limits.

Keywords-vertical profiling; CO₂ profile; sensors; discomfort index; NDIR

I. INTRODUCTION

Gas detection and precise monitoring are crucial in the environmental, mining, metrological, and agriculture sectors [1]. At present, there are many studies available on gas sensing technologies. The rapid changes in sensor technology from analog to digital sensors have promoted various levels of sensing from ppm (parts per million) to ppb (parts per billion) level [2]. The rise of Green House Gas (GHG) emissions globally (Figure 1) is caused by fossil fuel burning and, consequently, the increase in CO₂ levels worldwide. The concentrations of CO₂ emissions were highest in the year 2018,

and after the COVID-19 pandemic, the level has not reduced significantly [3]. The major reason behind these elevated levels of GHGs is the utilization of fossil fuels in non-organized sectors. These sectors mainly include concrete and energy-based industries. Power generation accounts for more than 50% of CO₂ emissions in India.

Changes in the CO₂ level affect the photosynthesis of plants. The negative ecological consequences of an increase in CO₂ levels are depicted in [4, 5]. Many research studies have analyzed and interpreted climate change and surface CO₂ level changes to understand the future predictions of global warming

and temperature change on this planet. The profiling of CO₂ at multiple altitudes is a novel attempt at environmental engineering.

The health burden of a city or town has always been challenging. The dispersion of CO₂ gas at various heights is critical concerning urban health. The dispersion of CO₂ gas at elevated heights is a critical indicator for urban health and the population in the area. The issues arising from atmospheric temperatures, like seasonal heat sensation and frequent changes in ambient temperature, are observed in various densely populated cities of the country. The existing AAQMS (Ambient Air Quality Monitoring Stations) provide data for air quality (AQ) and CO₂ levels [5-6]. These stations provide the data for a 1 km radius at ground level and are installed in limited locations. Hence, it becomes difficult to study accurate CO₂ levels in the AGL range in urban settings. The DI of the city is often calculated using data from a single or a few weather stations. In this DI calculation process, the data for the AGL range of CO₂, temperature and humidity are not considered. The degree of exposure due to multiple air pollutants at different heights can be accurately identified based on the measured data of pollutants at various AGL heights. Most air-quality drones are equipped with low-cost sensors. The sensors are attached to low-cost quadcopters without considering the aerodynamics of the drone. In such cases, the results may have errors.

Fig. 1. Global CO₂ level.

The measurement of CO₂ was first initiated in 1958 [7, 8]. After that, numerous measurement methods have been designed for vertical and horizontal profiling of air pollutants. In GHG and DI modelling predictions for meteorological applications, the data of CO₂, temperature, and humidity play a significant role. But the methods of CO₂ measurement, like tethered balloons or radiosonde, are not only costly and time-consuming, they are also complex in nature and difficult to implement practically [9, 10]. During the '80s, helicopters were employed for aerial surveys in residential and industrial settings. But with the introduction of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) for aerial surveys, monitoring gaseous concentrations became easier. Multirotor UAVs are categorized with regard to the number of rotors and their thrust (quadcopters, hexacopters, and octocopters), fixed wings, single rotor helicopter, fixed-wing hybrid VTOL, etc. Some early research was conducted with UAVs to understand the

vertical profile in the environment. In these research explorations, UAVs with fixed-wing planes were employed, and sensor mounting experiments were conducted. Due to the capacity of these UAVs to fly 1000 m AGL for more than 45 min, they were found to be very effective in meteorological applications. These UAVs had some drawbacks such as complexity in aerial operations, instability, maneuverability, slow speed of operation, stationary flights, etc., hence the sensor reading may get disturbed due to the non-holding/hovering position in the air. Table I [11, 12] depicts the comparison between fixed wing UAVs and multi-rotor UAVs.

TABLE I. FIXED-WING VS MULTI-ROTOR UAVS

Factors affecting environmental monitoring	Fixed wing platform	Multi-rotor UAV platform
Flight time	~ 50 min	~ 20 min
Altitude	High (~30,000 ft)	Low (~1,500– 11,150 ft)
Hovering and stability in 3D space	Low (can't hover at a fixed point)	High (in cm) using RTK
Sensor location	At tail/nose/onboard	Below frame/body
Take off / landing type	Horizontal (needs launching platform)	Vertical (does not need launching platform)
Take off area	Larger with takeoff strips	Very small with no takeoff strip
Learning curve and datasets	Larger and more complex datasets	Smaller and easier datasets

As shown in Figure 2, many researchers mounted the sensor onboard or kept the left side at the nose or below the frame of the drone [13, 14]. However, such experiments considered the downwash by the propellers. These drawbacks forced us to think of other simple options for monitoring CO₂ and other environmental pollutants like particulate matter, SO_x, NO_x, and CO.

Fig. 2. Positions used for sensor mounting.

A. The Role of DI

The DI is a parameter that indicates the human heat sensation in numerous climatic conditions. It is defined by:

$$DI = T - (0.55 - 0.0055 \times RH) (T - 14.5) \quad (1)$$

The existence of high-rise buildings, vegetation, and thermal discomfort sensation directly impact the DI. Therefore, the DI was first calculated using multiple altitude levels. Some studies reveal the direct impact of changes in surface temperature on the human body and comfort. "Stedman Heat Index" is the best example of quantifying the stress imposed on humans due to atmospheric moisture and temperature [15]. The

current study investigates the concentration of ambient CO₂ levels along with temperature and humidity [16]. The specific objectives of this experimental work were to examine the feasibility of UAVs (quadcopters) for environmental parameter monitoring purposes compared to the traditional available methods. Then the design of a standard protocol for drone-aided gas monitoring is discussed [16-18]. The calibration of the CO₂ sensor was targeted before tethering it near the drone [14]. Possible aerodynamic drag experiments were performed to attach the sensor module at multiple locations near the drone. The seasonal data were collected using the designed protocol.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Design of the Sensor Module

DJI Phantom 4 Pro, a quad-copter-based commercial model, was the UAV used in this study. This model is widely accepted and used for various research applications in air quality [18, 19]. The quadcopter with weight carrying capacity of 300 g for 20 min was sufficient for this application. The fundamental reason for the selection of this model was its excellent hovering altitude stability in aerial settings. A Non-Dispersive Infrared Detector (NDIR) sensor was employed for monitoring the levels of CO₂, temperature, relative humidity, and time logs in the memory card. This sensor has a detection range of 0-9999 ppm. The resolution of this instrument is 1 ppm. To hang below the drone, the sensor module weight was brought down below 200 g. For that purpose, a separate DC-DC step-down circuit was attached with the data logger to make it battery operated, as depicted in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. The sensor module.

B. Calibration of the CO₂ Sensor Module

For calibration of the CO₂ module, the CO₂ sensor was kept in the specially designed acrylic test chamber demonstrated in Figure 4. The closed test chamber has an arrangement of providing multiple gas standard spikes, a high-speed fan and dilation assembly for the internal environment. Initially, two sensors were kept in the test chamber. One was used in the drone and the other was the calibrated reference CO₂ sensor. Multiple known gas concentrations were spiked through the inlet of the test chamber and the concentration was recorded manually at an interval of 60 s [2]. Measurements of CO₂ were recorded for 60 min for each sensor. The calibration step was repeated in a monthly basis to assure a relation coefficient as near as possible to 1 [3].

Fig. 4. Calibration chamber.

C. Site Selection

The sensor module was cross verified with the other calibrated Testo 440 CO₂ sensor \pm (50 ppm) in the specially designed gas chamber unit. A customized sampling methodology was developed to avoid propellers' aerodynamic drag and thrust on sensors during data collection at multiple heights [20, 21]. To make it more interference-free from air flow, the sensor was hung with a fiber mesh. To assure errorless measurement, the readings of CO₂ sensor with and without the mesh were cross checked and found to be the same. To keep the sensor steady, a PVC pipe was employed. The position was identified using an anemometer and multiple aerodynamic studies in simulation software. The drone flight presented in this study took place at the CSIR-NEERI Nagpur campus. The coordinates for the location were 21.1238570 latitude and 79.0701430 longitude. This location was surrounded by a green zone and located in the central area of Nagpur city, Maharashtra, India. The study was carried out from December to May. Flights were taken, in a weekly basis, in the morning, afternoon, and evening hours from a predetermined location. The wind condition was normal during each flight. The area of the CSIR-NEERI campus is 100 acres. Figure 5 depicts the study location of the experimental work.

Fig. 5. Sitemap of the study area.

III. RESULTS

A. Sampling Protocol and Flight Path

The customized sampling protocol has been designed to measure gas concentrations at multiple heights. In most of the previous studies, it has been observed that the sensor array was mounted on the drone or in the vicinity of the landing gears of the quadcopter. This assembly is always made by neglecting the effect of downwash and thrust of the propellers. Apart from the propeller shape and size, the downwash effect deviates the sensor values during hovering and in-flight operations. Therefore, a novel sampling protocol has been designed as per the user's applications at the sampling site and pollutant matrix. As given in Figure 6, the protocol can be used at AGL meteorological data collection in open ground, green zones, and landfill sites with calm wind conditions.

Fig. 6. Drone-assisted sampling protocol.

The trajectory of the flight path was pre-identified. Therefore, the drone throttled upward from a fixed location and hovered at 5.0 m intervals. The drone was hovering at a location for 1.5 min at the sampling frequency as suggested by the DGCA guidelines. Figure 7 denotes the sensor's path and propeller impact analysis. It helps to minimize the dispersion effect in the horizontal plane. In the case of preferring a simple vertical path, there are chances of air dilution due to propellers. It can be observed in Figure 7(a) that maximum area was covered during vertical profiling. This path does not disturb the composition of the air due to shift in the horizontal position by 5 m. During the ascending flight, 1 min interval data were stored in a memory card, and after attending 60.0 m height, the descending data were collected and stored in a memory card. The flight path was plotted in MS-office toolbox and surfer software. It has been observed that the rotating propellers of the drone create a downwash effect in hovering instances. Hence CFD (Computational Fluid Dynamics) simulation of an axial

flow of drone propellers was conducted to study the downwash effect using the rotating region method. The simplified model of a rotating quadcopter was employed and simulated in air chamber. Airflow of 5000 mm × 5000 mm was employed in the chamber. This study aimed to find the region where the air affects minimally the sensor. As displayed in Figure 7(b), it could be observed that the quadcopter rotated at the height of 2625 mm with a maximum of 10,000 RPM. It was found that the region below 137.5 mm had the minimal impact of the propellers. Hence, the tethered distance was adjusted to 3048 mm away from the drone to avoid the impact of wind on CO₂ sensor. Tethering the sensor module away from the drone is a very simple technique that can be useful in many applications such as surface emissions monitoring, methane emission from municipal solid waste and landfill sites, and even volcanic eruptions monitoring.

Fig. 7. (a) Flight path adopted during data collection, (b) propellers' impact on sensor analysis.

B. Calibration of the Sensor Module

Figures 8-9 show the promising calibration results of the CO₂ sensor with the calibrated CO₂ meter. The R² value between the two sensors was 0.97929. The close chamber tests were repeatedly performed before each flight. This result shows that the mounted sensor module was accurate in the 3D space after mounting to the drone.

C. Seasonal Data Collection

The main objective was to formulate a sampling method for CO₂ detection using commercially available low-cost drones with accurate time-series data collection. The experimental design was made for two different seasons (winter and

summer) over urban locations and experiments separately for morning and evening hours. The idea was to check the difference (if any) in the daily pattern of vertical profiling.

Fig. 8. Closed chamber test.

Fig. 9. Time series plot.

Fig. 10. Altitude-wise temperature, humidity, and CO₂ levels during morning and evening-winter.

IV. DISCUSSION

During wintertime, the vertical profiling of CO₂, temperature and relative humidity was performed during the morning and evening hours. Temperature and CO₂ levels were negatively correlated (-0.2) and the relative humidity remained constant. During the morning, the inverse scenario prevails, the chances of pollutants being trapped under the inversion layer

are higher. That is why the concentration of CO₂ at 40-60 m AGL is found to be more in the morning than in the evening. The vertical profiling shows that the trend is opposite in the evening hours. The observations from the result are that temperature and CO₂ are positively correlated (+0.9), whereas relative humidity shows no significant relation with CO₂. During the evening, no exact inversion scenario occurs.

Fig. 11. Altitude-wise temperature, humidity, and CO₂ levels during morning and evening-summer.

Fig. 12. Winter and summer DI.

During summertime, the vertical profile of CO₂, temperature, and relative humidity shows that during the morning, temperature and CO₂ are negatively correlated, and relative humidity remains constant. During the morning time the inverse scenario increases. The chances of pollutants being trapped under the inversion layer are more, which is why the concentration of CO₂ at 40-60m AGL is found to be more than that of the evening. The vertical profiling of CO₂, temperature, and relative humidity shows the opposite trend during the evening hours. Temperature and CO₂ are positively correlated, whereas relative humidity shows no significant relation with CO₂ and remains constant and the inverse scenario occurs. The derived DI is maximum at 40-50 m height., DI during summertime mornings is maximum at the height of 0-10 m.

This methodology of pollutant data collection is feasible at the non-accessible locations of landfill sites, ecologically sensitive locations, volcanic eruptions, etc. According to the

protocol, the user must keep the sensor away from the drone. Therefore, there are minimum chances of interfering with the propellers and their effect on the sensors. Similarly, the drone can be protected during each survey, and users can change the sensor module each time as per their requirement for monitoring. The telescopic arm or pulley system can be attached to the drone to maintain the center of gravity of the drone. The proposed method is helpful in collecting the gaseous samples on varied heights and assures sample collection without any disturbance. The researchers optimized the process after experimentation and developed the SOP (Standard Operating Procedure). During this study it was observed that this experiment could not be carried out below 10 m/s wind velocity. The SOPs will be different for VOCs and particulate matter-based surveys.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The temperature and humidity profile of the atmospheric layer governs its stability. In addition, the concentration of some greenhouse gases (GHGs), like CO₂, varies with time and season as the atmospheric dynamics change. As the atmosphere warms due to the increased presence of GHGs (e.g. CO₂), its ability to carry moisture increases. This reflects increased stress on the human body. The DI gradually increases in tune with increased temperature and humidity. The CO₂ concentration decreases slowly from 20 m height in urban settings. Every area has buildings of varying heights, which impact the accumulation of pollutants. These pollutants have different concentrations in different height ranges. The heat reflection was monitored in 20 m AGL in urban settings. It was found that the drone flight should be below 5 m/s to avoid pendulum movement. In case of high-temperature locations like volcanic eruptions, MSW sites, etc., precautions and safety measures for the protection of sensors should be employed.

Extraction of this information from the atmosphere is a challenging and costly affair. The proposed methodology of vertical profiling will reduce error and provide accurate pollutant concentration data in 3D space. The current project's efforts have been made to materialize and validate a novel method for vertical profiling and information dissemination through sensor modules. In this regard, one derived parameter, DI, is formulated and studied over the urban setup during two seasons (winter and summer). The methodology employed in this study was found to be cost-effective and precise. This methodology can be applied autonomously in various environmental emission monitoring sectors like open cast mining emission monitoring, municipal solid waste gas emission analysis, and other surface-level harmful gas analyses. More research is required in the method development for drone-aided particulate matter monitoring.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. Kout, B. Bouaita, A. Beghriche, S. Labed, S. Chikhi, and E.-B. Bourenane, "A Hybrid Optimization Solution for UAV Network Routing," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 10270–10278, Apr. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5661>.
- [2] N. Harkat, A. Rahmane, and I. Bendjemila, "The Impact of Industrial Air Pollution on the Urban Environment of Setif: Modeling and Mapping of Total Suspended Particles," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 9431–9439, Dec. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5256>.
- [3] M. Alquraish and K. Abuhasel, "Sustainable Hybrid Design to Ensure Efficiency and Air Quality of Solar Air Conditioning," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 11036–11041, Jun. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5907>.
- [4] R. Mlambo, I. H. Woodhouse, F. Gerard, and K. Anderson, "Structure from Motion (SfM) Photogrammetry with Drone Data: A Low Cost Method for Monitoring Greenhouse Gas Emissions from Forests in Developing Countries," *Forests*, vol. 8, no. 3, Mar. 2017, Art. no. 68, <https://doi.org/10.3390/f8030068>.
- [5] S. Martin, J. Bange, and F. Beyrich, "Meteorological profiling of the lower troposphere using the research UAV 'M-AV Carolo,'" *Atmospheric Measurement Techniques*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 705–716, Apr. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-4-705-2011>.
- [6] J. G. J. Olivier and J. A. H. W. Peters, *Trends in global CO2 and total greenhouse gas emissions: 2019 Report*. Hague, Netherlands: PBL Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency, 2019.
- [7] R. Moriwaki and M. Kanda, "Vertical profiles of carbon dioxide, temperature, and water vapor within and above a suburban canopy layer in winter," presented at the Sixth Symposium on the Urban Environment, 14th Joint Conference on the Applications of Air Pollution Meteorology with the Air and Waste Management Association, 2006.
- [8] Z.-R. Peng, D. Wang, Z. Wang, Y. Gao, and S. Lu, "A study of vertical distribution patterns of PM2.5 concentrations based on ambient monitoring with unmanned aerial vehicles: A case in Hangzhou, China," *Atmospheric Environment*, vol. 123, pp. 357–369, Dec. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2015.10.074>.
- [9] D. C. Harris, "Charles David Keeling and the Story of Atmospheric CO2 Measurements," *Analytical Chemistry*, vol. 82, no. 19, pp. 7865–7870, Oct. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac1001492>.
- [10] A. Engel and U. Schmidt, "Vertical profile measurements of carbonylsulfide in the stratosphere," *Geophysical Research Letters*, vol. 21, no. 20, pp. 2219–2222, 1994, <https://doi.org/10.1029/94GL01461>.
- [11] J. Wivou, L. Udawatta, A. Alshehhi, E. Alzaabi, A. Albeloshi, and S. Alfalasi, "Air quality monitoring for sustainable systems via drone based technology," in *2016 IEEE International Conference on Information and Automation for Sustainability (ICIAFS)*, Galle, Sri Lanka, Sep. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIAFS.2016.7946542>.
- [12] D. R. Lyon, R. A. Alvarez, D. Zavala-Araiza, A. R. Brandt, R. B. Jackson, and S. P. Hamburg, "Aerial Surveys of Elevated Hydrocarbon Emissions from Oil and Gas Production Sites," *Environmental Science & Technology*, vol. 50, no. 9, pp. 4877–4886, May 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.6b00705>.
- [13] S.-J. Lu *et al.*, "Investigating the Role of Meteorological Factors in the Vertical Variation in PM2.5 by Unmanned Aerial Vehicle Measurement," *Aerosol and Air Quality Research*, vol. 19, no. 7, pp. 1493–1507, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.4209/aaqr.2018.07.0266>.
- [14] M. A. Boon, A. P. Drijfhout, and S. Tesfamichael, "Comparison of a Fixed-Wing and Multi-Rotor Uav for Environmental Mapping Applications: A Case Study," *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, vol. XLII-2-W6, pp. 47–54, Aug. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLII-2-W6-47-2017>.
- [15] "Welcome to DigitalSky," *DigitalSky*. <https://digitalsky.dgca.gov.in/home>.
- [16] E. Stott, R. D. Williams, and T. B. Hoey, "Ground Control Point Distribution for Accurate Kilometre-Scale Topographic Mapping Using an RTK-GNSS Unmanned Aerial Vehicle and SfM Photogrammetry," *Drones*, vol. 4, no. 3, Sep. 2020, Art. no. 55, <https://doi.org/10.3390/drones4030055>.

- [17] H. Xu, X. Hu, H. Guan, and G. He, "Development of a fine-scale discomfort index map and its application in measuring living environments using remotely-sensed thermal infrared imagery," *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 150, pp. 598–607, Sep. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2017.06.003>.
- [18] J. Wang *et al.*, "Simulation of diurnal variations of CO₂, water and heat fluxes over winter wheat with a model coupled photosynthesis and transpiration," *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*, vol. 137, no. 3, pp. 194–219, Apr. 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2006.02.007>.
- [19] M. Ray, P. Samal, and C. K. Panigrahi, "Implementation of a Hybrid Technique for the Predictive Control of the Residential Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning Systems," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 8772–8776, Jun. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5027>.
- [20] R. Wang, C. Zhao, W. Li, and Y. Qi, "Research on Thermal Comfort Equation of Comfort Temperature Range Based on Chinese Thermal Sensation Characteristics," in *Advances in Manufacturing, Production Management and Process Control*, 2020, pp. 254–265, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-20494-5_24.
- [21] C. Zhu *et al.*, "Carbon dioxide (CO₂) levels this century will alter the protein, micronutrients, and vitamin content of rice grains with potential health consequences for the poorest rice-dependent countries," *Science Advances*, vol. 4, no. 5, Dec. 2018, Art. no. eaaq1012, <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aaq1012>.

Bitcoin Price Prediction using the Hybrid Convolutional Recurrent Model Architecture

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ABSTRACT

The field of finance makes extensive use of real-time prediction of stock price tools, which are instruments that are put to use in the process of creating predictions. In this article, we attempt to predict the price of Bitcoin in a manner that is both accurate and reliable. Deep learning models, as opposed to more traditional methods, are used to manage enormous volumes of data and to generate predictions. The purpose of this research is to develop a method for predicting stock prices using the Hybrid Convolutional Recurrent Model (HCRM) architecture. This model architecture integrates the advantages of two separate deep learning models: The 1-Dimensional-Convolutional Neural Network (1D-CNN) and the Long-Short Term Memory (LSTM). The 1D-CNN is responsible for the feature extraction, while the LSTM is in charge of the temporal regression. The developed 1D-CNN-LSTM model has an outstanding performance in predicting stock values.

Keywords-1D-CNN; LSTM; Bitcoin; deep learning; prediction

I. INTRODUCTION

The future financial value of a company's stock, as predicted by its stock price, is important information for investors, shareholders, and organizations in order to maximize their returns and achieve their goals. The prediction of stock prices can be difficult by external elements, such as the velocity and volume of data, which make conducting and directing stock analysis and forecasting a difficult process [1]. The improvement in technology enables more precise information to be predicted, which is beneficial in the field of finance in order to grow and make decisions in accordance with that growth. Forecasting the movements of the stock market is a difficult effort due to the volatile nature of the market. When it comes to the development of significant trading techniques that may assist consumers in buying and selling stocks, the accuracy of stock prediction is a critical factor [2]. In general, the data on the stock market are plagued

by two primary issues: uncertainty and noise. The volatility in stock prices may be caused by many external factors. These may include market circumstances, the value of a firm, the political status, global events, etc. All these can have an impact on the trading of stocks on the stock market. The volatility, instability, and variability of the stock market, on the other hand, makes anticipating the future difficult and contributes to noisy data.

In order to predict how markets will behave in the future using data from the past and the present, researchers have developed various different models. The pattern of the data in regard to the temporal attribute is what is used to derive the behavior of the market. Due to the random fluctuations that occur over time, these temporal patterns provide changed obstacles in the process of computing the data regarding the stock market. Statistical procedures have been developed specifically for the purpose of computing such data.

Nevertheless, as time passes, not only does the market continue to develop and improve, but so too does the amount of data [3]. As investors from different countries come with their various interests, new global trades are born. When compared to traditional stock markets, making predictions on the Bitcoin market has a number of significant advantages. Bitcoin is not reliant on events in the marketplace or on the actions of interfering governments. The limited availability of the coins serves as the primary factor in establishing its price [4].

Bitcoin is a crypto currency that is used globally for digital payments and investments. Because Bitcoins are decentralized and not affiliated with any government, it is incredibly easy and quick to use them to make financial transactions. The term "bitcoin exchanges" refers to a number of different online markets that are up for business for investors to use. Users have the ability to purchase and sell Bitcoins using a wide variety of currencies as a result of this feature. When they are not being used, Bitcoins are stored in a digital wallet, which is effectively the same thing as having an online bank account. Blockchain is the name of the location where the records of all of the transactions and the data about the timestamps are stored. Each individual entry in a blockchain is referred and stated to as a block. Each block has a pointer that refers to a data block that came before it. The information stored on blockchains is encoded. During transactions, the user's name will never be disclosed; just their wallet ID will be shared with the other parties.

In this paper, we present the Hybrid Convolutional Recurrent Model (HCRM) architecture by combining the 1-D-CNN and the LSTM for stock price prediction. The 1D-CNN is used for feature extraction and the LSTM is used for the temporal regression task.

II. RELATED WORKS

This section provides a concise summary of the previous research on the application of deep learning to the prediction of Bitcoin prices. Authors in [5] introduced two prediction models based on Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) and LSTM, and they compared them with the Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model, which is a commonly used time series forecasting model. They used the information on the price of Bitcoin to develop classification models, which make predictions about whether the price will increase or decrease in the future based on historical values. It was demonstrated that the RNN and LSTM models are superior to the ARIMA model. The number of Bitcoin wallets and unique addresses, the difficulty of mining blocks, the hash rate, and other aspects of the Bitcoin blockchain were examined in [6] in addition to the price data. The authors used these features, which are highly correlated with the Bitcoin price, to create prediction models. They investigated a number of different regression models, including linear regression, random forests, gradient boosting, and neural networks. In addition to the data from the blockchain, authors in [7] also took into account several macroeconomic factors, including the S&P 500, Euro STOXX 50, DOW 30, and NASDAQ, as well as the exchange rates between the major fiat currencies. They studied three different prediction models based on a Bayesian Neural Network (BNN), linear regression, and Support Vector Regression

(SVR), and they found that the BNN performed better than the other two prediction models. Authors in [8] developed a rolling window LSTM model and showed that it outperformed the prediction models that were based on linear regression, SVR, neural networks, and LSTM. Authors in [9] introduced a deep learning-based random sampling model and demonstrated that it performed better than LSTM-based models. Authors in [10] looked at social data in an attempt to forecast the variations in the price of bitcoin. The proposed model in [11] overcomes the instability in prediction. The authors manually adjusted the DNN hyperparameters, such as the model's number of layers, learning rate, neurons, and number of epochs, for greater accuracy. The metrics MAE and RMSE were used for the evaluation of the hybrid stock price model and the results were satisfying. Authors in [12] created a revolutionary hybrid deep learning approach with the purpose of forecasting stock market prices. A hybrid model was created for this purpose by combining Bi-LSTM and GRU networks with three layers of dense units. They also used the same datasets to create other cutting-edge predictive deep learning networks for comparison. The suggested hybrid model outperforms previous deep learning models for ASIANPAINT business starting prices derived from NIFTY-50 stock data.

III. METHODOLOGY

CNNs and RNNs are two varieties of neural networks that can be utilized for prediction tasks. These deep learning networks are also capable of being utilized in predicting systems for the stock market. In this article, we propose a new model for predicting stock prices using convolutional recurrent hybridization as the underlying algorithm. The 1D-CNN-LSTM model structure is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. The proposed 1D-CNN-LSTM model structure.

A. 1D-CNN

CNNs are among the most effective deep learning techniques and have found widespread application in a many computer vision applications. The conventional architecture of a CNN consists of a stack of convolution and pooling layers. The primary purpose of this succession of layers is to extract high-level features, which, in contrast to traditional approaches to machine learning, removes the need for a stage that involves manually engineering features. The pooling layers can reduce the size of the feature map that the convolutional layers generate. At the very end of the network, there is an attachment of several fully linked layers. The purpose of this attachment is to produce the final output and introduce nonlinearity into the network [13]. CNNs, in general, anticipate a 2D input for processing, such as images, but they can be adjusted to analyze 1D data, such as time series financial or stock data. Images are an example of a 2D input. In the current study, we used 1D-CNN to process the historical data that were read. The structure of the incoming stock data was taken into consideration when selecting the convolutional kernels as well [14].

B. LSTM

The deep RNN family includes LSTM. The LSTM algorithm was developed specifically for the analysis of sequential data. It is possible that the addition of a variety of gates to its architecture will enable it to recall more extensive data histories. It is capable of resolving the difficulties that typical RNNs face, such as gradient vanishing and gradient explosion. The gates are responsible for determining how the information will move through the network. The amount of information taken from history that will be stored is determined by the Input Gate. The amount of information that can be forgotten from previous moments is determined by the Forget Gate, while the Output Gates are responsible for controlling the internal memory unit, which is responsible for producing the required quantity of information for the subsequent cycle [15].

C. Structure and Learning

Following a series of intensive experiments, we came to the conclusion that the best potential 1D-CNN-LSTM design is one that has one 1D-convolutional layer in addition to one 1D-max pooling layer. The 1D-CNN layer's settings include a kernel size of 2, strides of 1, a rectified linear unit (ReLU) as the activation function, and a filter size set to 64. In the end, we came up with the optimum LSTM architecture, which consists of two layers of sequential LSTMs and two levels of dense layers. In the tests that we ran, we used a value of 100 for the number of units in both LSTM layers. Additionally, the "return_sequence" argument was given the value of true for the first LSTM layer and false for the second layer. This was done to ensure that each cell in the layer returned all of the outputs from the unrolled LSTM cell so that we could compare these outputs at each time step with the very next price in the sequence. At the very end, the network consists of two dense layers that follow one another for the purpose of making a final regression prediction. In the first dense layer, there are 25 neurons, and in the final dense layer, there is just one neuron. Also, we employed the Adam optimizer with a batch size of 32 and the Mean Squared Error (MSE) as our loss function.

IV. RESULTS

The data were gathered from the Yahoo Finance website, in the form of a time series. The historical data ranged from November 17, 2014, to December 31, 2022. Following the gathering of the data, a stage known as preprocessing was performed in order to rid the data of any missing values or noise and choose the features that will be utilized (feature extraction). We divided the data to 80% training and 20% testing subsets. We were unable to employ random splitting when dividing the data into training and validation sets since doing this will eliminate the time factor [16]. Therefore, we used the first 80% of the dataset to train the model, and the last 20% to test it. The outcome was evaluated with the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE). The RMSE statistic determines how well a model can forecast a continuous variable. Because the RMSE units are the same units as the dependent objective of your data, it is possible to utilize this information to determine whether or not the magnitude of the error has any significance. The RMSE should be as low as possible for the model to have the best performance [17].

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{t=1}^n (\text{predicted}(t) - \text{actual}(t))^2}{n}} \quad (1)$$

We selected the following number of epochs: 50, 100, 150, 200, and 250. According to Table I, the results are more conservative when using 150 epochs.

TABLE I. RMSE RESULTS VS NUMBER OF EPOCHS

No.	Epoch No.	RMSE
1	50	603.40959
2	100	443.38573
3	150	37.13838
4	200	925.09971
5	250	1179.22304

The results provided in Figure 2 were generated by making predictions using the proposed model with 150 epochs. The green line represents the result of a close prediction, while the blue and yellow lines represent the results of data training.

V. CONCLUSION

The proposed 1D-CNN-LSTM model was successful in predicting the bitcoin value in the Yahoo Finance stock market. Our model, which makes use of the time series approach, was able to construct and produce results, and those results that were able to predict the price for the upcoming days. On the other hand, the result was not satisfactory in terms of RMSE, which is a drawback. It is worth mentioning that the stock markets are affected by a variety of factors, including political and economic issues that might have an impact on either the local or global level. Therefore, the price prediction of bitcoin with the use of any model cannot be perfectly precise.

In future work, emphasis will be placed on a large number of additional deep learning layers, the addition of dropout, the modification of the number of epochs, and the utilization of a variety of unstable datasets in order to evaluate the prediction accuracy.

Fig. 2. Prediction result of the price of bitcoin on epoch 150.

REFERENCES

- [1] O. B. Sezer, M. U. Gudelek, and A. M. Ozbayoglu, "Financial time series forecasting with deep learning: A systematic literature review: 2005–2019," *Applied Soft Computing*, vol. 90, May 2020, Art. no. 106181, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asoc.2020.106181>.
- [2] W. Long, Z. Lu, and L. Cui, "Deep learning-based feature engineering for stock price movement prediction," *Knowledge-Based Systems*, vol. 164, pp. 163–173, Jan. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.knsys.2018.10.034>.
- [3] Y. Kara, M. Acar Boyacioglu, and Ö. K. Baykan, "Predicting direction of stock price index movement using artificial neural networks and support vector machines: The sample of the Istanbul Stock Exchange," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 38, no. 5, pp. 5311–5319, May 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2010.10.027>.
- [4] U. P. Gurav and S. Kotrappa, "Sentiment Aware Stock Price Forecasting using an SA-RNN-LBL Learning Model," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 6356–6361, Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3805>.
- [5] S. McNally, J. Roche, and S. Caton, "Predicting the Price of Bitcoin Using Machine Learning," in *2018 26th Euromicro International Conference on Parallel, Distributed and Network-based Processing (PDP)*, Cambridge, UK, Mar. 2018, pp. 339–343, <https://doi.org/10.1109/PDP2018.2018.00060>.
- [6] M. Saad, J. Choi, D. Nyang, J. Kim, and A. Mohaisen, "Toward Characterizing Blockchain-Based Cryptocurrencies for Highly Accurate Predictions," *IEEE Systems Journal*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 321–332, Mar. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/JSYST.2019.2927707>.
- [7] H. Jang and J. Lee, "An Empirical Study on Modeling and Prediction of Bitcoin Prices With Bayesian Neural Networks Based on Blockchain Information," *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 5427–5437, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2017.2779181>.
- [8] J. Huisu, J. Lee, H. Ko, and W. Lee, "Predicting bitcoin prices by using rolling window LSTM model," in *Proceedings of the KDD data science in Fintech Workshop*, London, UK, Aug. 2018, pp. 19–23.
- [9] T. Shintate and L. Pichl, "Trend Prediction Classification for High Frequency Bitcoin Time Series with Deep Learning," *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, vol. 12, no. 1, Mar. 2019, Art. no. 17, <https://doi.org/10.3390/jrfm12010017>.
- [10] Y. B. Kim *et al.*, "Predicting Fluctuations in Cryptocurrency Transactions Based on User Comments and Replies," *PLOS ONE*, vol. 11, no. 8, 2016, Art. no. e0161197, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0161197>.
- [11] Srivinay, B. C. Manujakshi, M. G. Kabadi, and N. Naik, "A Hybrid Stock Price Prediction Model Based on PRE and Deep Neural Network," *Data*, vol. 7, no. 5, May 2022, Art. no. 51, <https://doi.org/10.3390/data7050051>.
- [12] Md. E. Karim, Md. Foysal, and S. Das, "Stock Price Prediction Using Bi-LSTM and GRU-Based Hybrid Deep Learning Approach," in *Proceedings of Third Doctoral Symposium on Computational Intelligence*, Singapore, 2023, pp. 701–711, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-3148-2_60.
- [13] O. Ahmed and A. Brifcani, "Gene Expression Classification Based on Deep Learning," in *2019 4th Scientific International Conference Najaf (SICN)*, Al-Najef, Iraq, Apr. 2019, pp. 145–149, <https://doi.org/10.1109/SICN47020.2019.9019357>.
- [14] D. K. Suker, "Deep Learning CNN for the Prediction of Grain Orientations on EBSD Patterns of AA5083 Alloy," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 8393–8401, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4807>.
- [15] N. T. T. Vu, N. P. Tran, and N. H. Nguyen, "Recurrent Neural Network-based Path Planning for an Excavator Arm under Varying Environment," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 7088–7093, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4125>.
- [16] F. Qian and X. Chen, "Stock Prediction Based on LSTM under Different Stability," in *2019 IEEE 4th International Conference on Cloud Computing and Big Data Analysis (ICCCBDA)*, Chengdu, China, Apr. 2019, pp. 483–486, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCCBDA.2019.8725709>.
- [17] M. Çalasan, S. H. E. Abdel Aleem, and A. F. Zobaa, "On the root mean square error (RMSE) calculation for parameter estimation of photovoltaic models: A novel exact analytical solution based on Lambert W function," *Energy Conversion and Management*, vol. 210, Apr. 2020, Art. no. 112716, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2020.112716>.

A BiLSTM-CF and BiGRU-based Deep Sentiment Analysis Model to Explore Customer Reviews for Effective Recommendations

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ABSTRACT

The advancement of technology has led to the rise of social media forums and e-commerce platforms, which have become popular means of communication, and people can express their opinions through comments and reviews. Increased accessibility to online feedback helps individuals make informed decisions about product purchases, services, and other decisions. This study used a sentiment analysis-based approach to improve the functionality of the recommendations from user reviews and consider the features (aspects and opinions) of products and services to understand the characteristics and attributes that influence the performance of classification algorithms. The proposed model consists of data preprocessing, word embedding, character representation creation, feature extraction using BiLSTM-CF, and classification using BiGRU. The proposed model was evaluated on different multidomain benchmark datasets demonstrating impressive performance. The proposed model outperformed existing models, offering more promising performance results in recommendations.

Keywords-sentiment analysis; reviews; classification; deep learning; recommendations

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid and continuous growth of the Internet has resulted in the migration of a multitude of applications from the physical to the digital realm [1]. Various sectors, such as e-commerce, banking, multimedia consumption, and service bookings, have experienced this transition, altering the way people access information. In the physical world, people typically rely on a limited number of resources to search for information. For example, to purchase a mobile phone, one

may visit multiple electronic stores, seek information from sales assistants about phone specifications and recommendations, and ultimately choose after a few consultations. However, the overwhelming abundance of online content, particularly unstructured text and online reviews, is overflowing the Web. Online reviews play a crucial role for users who need to make decisions among various options, such as purchasing a product, watching a movie, or selecting a restaurant [2]. Through these reviews, users express

their opinions about different items and their respective aspects, including characteristics, features, attributes, or components. Typically written in free text format, reviews require users to carefully read and analyze them to identify expressed opinions and discover the strengths and weaknesses of the available items to make informed decisions [3].

Recommendation systems aim to offer personalized recommendations for most items to address the challenge of information overload and assist users in decision-making tasks. Recommendation systems, which were developed in the 1990s and rely on user preferences and ratings, have experienced significant growth and widespread adoption over the past few decades [4-5]. Today, they are essential in various industries, including e-commerce, health, telecoms, etc. For instance, Amazon, YouTube, and Twitter use recommendation systems to suggest popular products, recommend related videos, and offer connections with people and pages to follow, respectively. Recommendation systems can derive significant benefits from incorporating sentiment analysis [6]. Sentiment analysis is the process of extracting sentiments/opinions from user text [7]. There are two categories of sentiments: binary and multi-sentiments. Binary sentiments are positive or negative, while multi-sentiments include happy, angry, upset, dull, etc. Existing approaches in recommendation systems use sentiment analysis at the sentence or document level. However, the modern Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis (ABSA) is used less in recommendation systems [8].

Existing sentiment analysis methods are domain-oriented and face the challenges of subjective sentences and slang words in user reviews [9-10]. This reduces the accuracy of sentiment analysis and, as a result, the recommendations of products. This study proposes a hybrid deep learning model for product recommendation using ABSA to overcome these challenges. Using ABSA models, recommendation systems can effectively address the data sparsity issue commonly encountered in traditional recommendation systems. Therefore, integrating sentiment analysis at the aspect level into recommendation systems can significantly enhance the quality of recommendations provided to users. The main contributions of this study are:

- Consideration of the features (aspects and opinions) of products and services that help to understand the characteristics and attributes that influence the performance of classification algorithms when dealing with product reviews.
- The proposal of a transformer-based hybrid model that uses Concurrent Neural Networks, Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory, and Conditional Random Field (CNN-BiLSTM-CRF) for feature extraction and Bidirectional Gated Recurrent Unit (BiGRU) for classification.
- The results of the proposed method were compared with baseline approaches, demonstrating its superior results.

II. BACKGROUND STUDY

Sentiment analysis holds immense value across various domains, such as business, government, and education, and has been proven incredibly useful. Extensive research has

investigated the use of sentiment analysis in recommendation systems. In [11], data from Twitter-based airline discussions were analyzed using various features with data mining algorithms. The findings showed that emoticons played a significant role in determining the conveyed sentiment, surpassing the influence of textual data analysis. In [12], LSTM was combined with Word2Vec representation to improve sentiment analysis performance, showing that the LSTM gating mechanism during training contributed to improved results, outperforming other baseline models. In [13], a Bi-LSTM model was presented for opinion mining of reviews. The dataset consisted of 23,485 assessments classified into three categories based on their negative, neutral, and positive rating points. The data were cleaned by tokenizing and removing special characters from the reviews. Word embeddings were also generated using a Word2Vec pre-trained model. In [14], a nearest-neighbor-based approach was used for feature selection, calculating distance metrics and cosine similarity on preprocessed data. The primary goal was to improve performance by optimizing feature selection and tuning hyperparameters, involving various feature vectorization methods to achieve higher accuracy.

In [15], the efficiency of various machine-learning models was evaluated for classifying sentiments, showing that the Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) model demonstrated the most exceptional performance, having a remarkable accuracy of 85.4% in sentiment analysis. In [16], a combined CNN and BiLSTM model, called ConvBiLSTM, was proposed for sentiment analysis. The CNN layer receives feature embeddings as input and outputs lower-level features, while BiLSTM is used for classification. In [17], a sentiment analysis was carried out on Weibo posts about travelers' experiences with commercial air travel. This study used a multitask structural arrangement to evaluate events and sentiments simultaneously. This model achieved 89% accuracy but struggled with out-of-vocabulary words, limiting its performance and adaptability to dynamic language. In [18], a mixed-fusion architecture was proposed for image-text sentiment analysis, leveraging the correlation between visual and semantic content. This model achieved 76% accuracy for Twitter data and 87% for Getty photos but was costly and time-consuming due to the search for opinionated words. In [19], extensive social information was incorporated for multimodal sentiment analysis using regional attention and a heterogeneous relation network. This model achieved 87% accuracy but lost some features during extraction, potentially losing important information and reducing predictive power.

In [20], ABSA-PER was introduced, which was a model designed for polarity estimation of reviews through ABSA. Experimental results demonstrated that ABSA-PER outperformed the baseline methods, achieving a remarkable 86.5% accuracy for polarity calculation. In [21], a novel approach was proposed, called lexical attention and aspect-oriented GCN. This method involved constructing an aspect-oriented dependency-parsed tree that is crucial in calculating sentiment scores. Then, an aspect-oriented GCN extracts weighted lexical features specific to each aspect. The proposed approach was used in three datasets and, by considering lexical

properties and aspect-specific dependencies, achieved promising results in sentiment polarity prediction for different aspects within the text. In [22], a meta-ensemble deep learning approach was proposed that combined multiple deep learning models trained with different meta-learners. This approach was experimentally shown to outperform baseline deep learning models, especially when trained with probability class distributions.

III. METHODOLOGY

The proposed approach revolves around three key components: Data Processing, Feature Extraction, and Sentiment Classification. Since e-commerce platforms host

user-generated content, it is necessary to preprocess textual reviews to ensure their cleanliness before extracting meaningful features. Then, advanced language representation models, namely BERT, and CNN, were used for word embedding and character representation, respectively. Then, BiLSTM with CRF was used for feature extraction, which is well-suited for sequential data processing. Lastly, BiGRU was used to classify the sentiments. This approach effectively captured contextual dependencies and performed superior sentiment analysis using bidirectional information flow in the Recurrent Neural Network (RNN). Figure 1 shows the proposed model.

Fig. 1. The proposed model.

A. Data Preprocessing

Data preprocessing is an important step in preparing text for classification, particularly in online contexts where noise and irrelevant content can be prevalent. This noise may include HTML tags, advertisements, and other distracting elements [23]. Moreover, words within the text often have minimal impact on the classification task but still contribute to the overall complexity because each word is treated as a distinct dimension. The fundamental assumption behind effective data preprocessing is that reducing text noise can improve classifier performance and sentiment analysis results [11]. The entire approach to data preprocessing consists of several essential steps. The first step involves cleaning the online text, removing unwanted elements such as HTML tags and advertisements, and ensuring that only the relevant text remains for further analysis. Next, focus is given to removing unnecessary white

spaces within the text, as they do not contribute to the meaning or the classification task. Expanding abbreviations is another important preprocessing step, as many texts contain abbreviated words or acronyms that can be difficult for classification algorithms to interpret accurately. Expanding these abbreviations to their full forms facilitates better comprehension and analysis of the text.

Sentences can be categorized into two types: subjective and objective. Subjective sentences convey positive or negative opinions, while objective sentences do not express any opinions [20]. Objective sentences are usually facts or universal truths. For example, "I love the world" is considered subjective, but "The sun is hot" must be considered an objective statement. Therefore, it is necessary to remove the objective sentences from the dataset. This step improves the accuracy of the sentiment analysis. A lexicon, SentiWordNET

3.0, calculates the subjectivity score and provides the negative and positive scores of words [3]. The subjectivity score is calculated using the following equation:

$$Sub\ Score = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^n (w_{pos} + w_{neg})}{n} \quad (1)$$

where w_{pos} and w_{neg} are the positive and negative scores of the words and n represents the total number of words present in the review.

B. Feature Extraction and Selection

The most suitable and optimal features (aspects and opinions) are important for successful sentiment analysis. The feature extraction and selection phase is carried out using the hybrid deep learning technique BiLSTM-CRF. Two different word representations are used to feed Bi-LSTM-CRF for feature extraction: word embedding using BERT and character-level representation using CNN. To generate word embeddings, the BERT tokenizer is used first to tokenize the input text into individual words or subwords, and then the tokenized input is passed through the BERT model to generate a sequence of hidden states [24]. The dot product of these concealed states and a learned weight matrix can then be used to generate word embeddings for every word in the input text. The BERT word embeddings are particularly useful because they are context-aware, meaning that the embedding for a word can vary depending on the context in which it appears. This contrasts with many other word embedding methods, which generate a fixed embedding for each word regardless of context.

Previous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of CNN in extracting morphological information, such as prefixes or suffixes of words, from individual characters and encoding it into neural representations [25]. This study adopted a similar CNN architecture with the distinction that character embeddings were used solely as inputs to the CNN, omitting character-type features. Additionally, a dropout layer was applied before feeding the character embeddings into the CNN [26]. Finally, the neural network model was constructed by feeding the BLSTM output vectors into a CRF layer. Figure 2 shows the architecture of the framework in detail, with CNN-computed character-level representations for each word using BERT-generated character embeddings as input. The character-level representation vector and the word embedding vector are combined and provided as input to the BLSTM network.

BLSTM is an RNN variant that combines the properties of both forward and backward LSTMs [13]. In traditional LSTM, the input sequence undergoes forward processing, with each time step receiving information from the preceding time step. However, in natural language processing, information from past and future time steps can prove to be useful. To overcome the limitation of being unable to capture information from past and future contexts, BLSTM was designed with two hidden layers in its architecture: one layer operates on the input in the forward direction, and the other layer processes it in the backward direction. As the backward layer processes the sequence in reverse order, it can effectively capture information from both past and future contexts. By combining the outputs of both the forward and backward layers, BLSTM

can model the dependencies in both directions, rendering it particularly useful for tasks that require understanding a sequence's context, such as speech recognition, sentiment analysis, named entity recognition, and many more.

Fig. 2. Feature extraction framework.

The output vectors produced by BiLSTM are subsequently fed into the CRF layer to determine the most suitable features. CRF is a probabilistic graphical model particularly used in sequence labeling problems [27]. In sequence labeling, the goal is to assign a label or category to each element in a sequence of observations. For example, in natural language processing, sequence labeling can involve assigning part-of-speech tags to each word in a sentence or identifying entities such as person names, locations, or dates. The output of the CRF layers is the suitable features, i.e., aspects and opinions.

C. Classification

GRU exhibits a simpler structure compared to LSTM, making it relatively easier to train. Specifically, BiGRU integrates gates that suppress information loss. It consolidates the output and forget gates in LSTM to create an update gate, streamlining the structure of BiGRU and significantly saving disk space [28]. The BiGRU model effectively highlights significant information present in a text by generating output in both forward and backward directions.

The GRU model automatically learns which resources are essential and which can be eliminated during training, making it potentially more effective in handling extended texts. However, a one-way GRU network can miss important information in text sentiment analysis because its states are always from the front to the back. Research evidence strongly suggests that BiGRU outperforms GRU [28]. BiGRU consists of two unidirectional GRUs that operate in opposite directions, forward and backward, as shown in Figure 3. Both GRU layers in the BiGRU model simultaneously use all resources that flow through the network. At each moment, the input is fed into both GRUs simultaneously but in opposite directions. The result is jointly determined to improve accuracy.

Fig. 3. BiGRU framework.

The BiGRU network consists of an input layer, a forward GRU, a reverse GRU, and a forward GRU output layer. This intricate network is designed to transmit data to both the forward GRU and the reverse GRU from the input layer, and these two powerful GRUs work together to determine the output sequence jointly. The following expression represents the BiGRU layer:

$$\vec{h}_t = \text{Gru}(x_t, \vec{h}_t - 1)$$

$$\overleftarrow{h}_t = \text{Gru}(x_t, \overleftarrow{h}_t - 1)$$

$$h_t = f(W \vec{h}_t \overleftarrow{h}_t + W \overleftarrow{h}_t \vec{h}_t + b_t)$$

where t is time, \vec{h}_t is positive layers' state at time t , \overleftarrow{h}_t is negative layers' state at time t , $W \vec{h}_t$ is the weight of the positive hidden layer, $W \overleftarrow{h}_t$ is the weight of the negative hidden layer, and b_t is the hidden layer bias at time t .

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A series of experiments were carried out to evaluate the accuracy and efficacy of the proposed model. The experimental evaluation demonstrated that the proposed method significantly outperformed the existing cutting-edge methods.

A. Dataset

The proposed model was evaluated using three benchmark datasets from different domains: products, hotels, and movie reviews. The product reviews dataset consists of reviews of five distinct products: Canon, Nikon, MP3 Players, Nokia 6610, and Apex AD 2600 [29]. The hotel review dataset originated from tripadvisor.com [30]. Lastly, the movie reviews dataset was obtained from the large movie review dataset used by Stanford University's AI department [31]. Table I shows the details of the datasets.

TABLE I. DATASET BREAKDOWN

#	Dataset	Review type	Reviews about	Reviews
1	DS 1	Products	Canon, Nikon, MP3 Players, Nokia 6610, Apex AD 2600	3,552
2	DS 2	Hotels	Hotels	20,490
3	DS 3	Movies	Movies	50,000

B. Results

K-fold cross-validation was used to validate the results of the proposed model. At first, the dataset was divided into K bins of identical sizes, where one bin was allocated for testing and the other $K-1$ bins were used for training purposes [3]. This process was executed on a GeForce GTX 1080 TiGPU. The parameters used were a batch size of 64, a learning rate of $3e^{-5}$, a dropout rate of 0.3, and 16 epochs. Performance was evaluated using three key metrics: accuracy, recall, and precision. Table II presents the results. When applied to DS 1, the proposed model achieved 92.56% accuracy, 91.32% precision, and 91.82% recall. In DS 2, the proposed BERT-CNN model achieved 91.8% accuracy, 91.05% precision, and 91.34% recall. Finally, in DS 3, it obtained an accuracy of 90.85%, an exceptional precision of 98.22%, and a recall of 89.45%. These results indicate that the proposed model accurately identified sentiments and aspects across all three datasets, showing remarkably high precision while maintaining a respectable recall rate, thereby affirming its potential as an efficient tool for sentiment analysis in a variety of domains.

TABLE II. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

#	Dataset	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)
1	DS 1 (product reviews)	92.56	91.32	91.82
2	DS 2 (hotel reviews)	91.82	91.05	91.34
3	DS 3 (movie reviews)	90.85	89.22	89.45

Another experiment was carried out to assess the performance of BERT-CNN on the three datasets, using standard word embedding models, namely Global Vectors for word representation (GloVe) and Word2Vec, which are well-known methods for constructing word embeddings [32]. GloVe is a word embedding model that learns word vectors by analyzing co-occurrence statistics in a corpus, thereby encoding global and local word relationships. Word2Vec, is a word embedding model that learns word vectors by predicting adjacent words or contexts in a corpus, producing vector representations that encode semantic relationships and word similarities [33]. Table III provides a comparison of the proposed BERT-CNN approach with GloVe and Word2Vec.

TABLE III. COMPARISON OF THE PROPOSED APPROACH WITH GLOVE AND WORD2VEC

#	Word Embeddings	Accuracy	Precision	Recall
DS 1 (Product Reviews)				
1	Glove	82.79%	82.12	82.53
2	Word2Vec	78.28%	77.56	77.86
3	BERT-CNN (proposed)	92.56%	91.32	91.82
DS 2 (Hotel Reviews)				
1	Glove	80.65%	80.01	80.42
2	Word2Vec	74.28%	73.51	73.81
3	BERT-CNN (proposed)	91.82%	91.05	91.34
DS 3 (Movie Reviews)				
1	Glove	81.32%	80.48	81.03
2	Word2Vec	75.36%	74.65	74.32
3	BERT-CNN (proposed)	90.85%	89.22	89.45

The results show that the proposed BERT-CNN model consistently outperformed the baseline word embedding models across the three different domain datasets. This implies that the BERT-CNN model performs well and effectively captures contextual information and features from user reviews. These results highlight its potential to enhance various natural language processing tasks, indicating its superiority over traditional word embedding approaches.

The effectiveness of the proposed model was assessed in contrast to some of the latest baseline models. Table IV shows the comparisons in all datasets in terms of accuracy. BERT-SKG [34] integrates sentiment domain knowledge with BERT and generates embedding vectors that align entities in the sentiment knowledge graph. LSIBA-ENN [35] introduces a novel model designed to analyze online product reviews. ARM-BERT [36] proposed POS-ARM with BERT for ABSA. Finally, LeBERT [37] integrates N-grams, BERT lexicon, and CNN for sentiment classification in reviews.

TABLE IV. COMPARISON OF THE PROPOSED APPROACH WITH BASELINE APPROACHES IN TERMS OF ACCURACY

#	Approaches	DS 1	DS 2	DS 3
		Accuracy (%)		
1	BERT-SKG	89.24	88.12	88.34
2	LSIBA-ENN	90.31	89.31	89.16
3	ARM-BERT	91.80	91.23	90.07
4	LeBERT	88.20	88.72	88.42
5	Proposed	92.56	91.82	90.85

The BERT-SKG approach achieved an average accuracy of 88.90%, having its highest accuracy of 89.24% in DS 1, followed by 88.34% in DS 3, and 88.12% in DS 2. Although BERT-SKG performed reasonably well, it had slightly lower accuracy than the other approaches. The LSIBA-ENN approach showed better performance with an average accuracy of 89.26%, showing its highest accuracy of 90.31% in DS 1, followed by 89.31% in DS 2, and 89.16% in DS 3. These results indicate that LSIBA-ENN outperformed BERT-SKG in all three datasets. The ARM-BERT approach demonstrated even higher accuracy, averaging 91.03%, having an impressive accuracy of 91.80% in DS 1, followed by 91.23% in DS 2, and a slightly lower accuracy of 90.07% in DS 3. ARM-BERT outperformed both BERT-SKG and LSIBA-ENN, indicating superior performance in sentiment analysis tasks. LeBERT achieved an average accuracy of 88.45%, having the highest accuracy of 88.72% in DS 2, followed by 88.20% in DS 1, and 88.42% in DS 3. Although LeBERT performed reasonably well, it fell behind the ARM-BERT approach, which achieved higher accuracies across all datasets. Finally, the proposed model outperformed all other approaches, achieving an impressive average accuracy of 91.41%, having the highest accuracy of 92.56% in DS 1, followed by 91.82% in DS 2, and 90.85% in DS 3.

Figure 4 shows the comparison results of the proposed method with other baseline approaches in terms of accuracy, precision, and recall. The proposed model outperformed the other approaches in different domain datasets, showcasing its effectiveness in sentiment analysis and recommendation systems. ARM-BERT also showed strong performance,

outperforming BERT-SKG, LSIBA-ENN, and LeBERT. LSIBA-ENN and LeBERT showed decent results, while BERT-SKG lagged slightly behind. The performance of the proposed model stems from its effective feature extraction and selection methods, as it uses word embedding with BERT, character representation through CNN, feature extraction with BiLSTM-CRF, and classification with BiGRU. BiGRU operates in both forward and backward directions in the input sequence, allowing it to capture contextual information from preceding and subsequent contexts. This comprehensive approach facilitates understanding of word dependencies and capturing the overall sentiment expressed in sentences. Therefore, the proposed model acts as an efficient system for recommending products, movies, and hotels.

Fig. 4. (a) DS 1, (b) DS 2, and (c) DS 3 results comparison.

V. CONCLUSION

Sentiment analysis is important in offering recommendations for various products and services, as it empowers individuals to perceive and use customers' opinions, emotions, and attitudes toward them. This study presented an innovative approach to sentiment analysis in recommendation systems by implementing hybrid deep-learning models. The proposed method extracted features using BiLSTM-CRF and performed classification using BiGRU. An experimental evaluation was conducted on three multidomain benchmark

datasets on product, hotel, and movie reviews. The proposed model demonstrated superior performance compared to the BERT-SKG, ARM-BERT, and LeBERT approaches, since it achieved accuracy of 92.56% in the product reviews dataset, 91.82% in the hotel reviews dataset, and 90.85% in the movie reviews dataset. The results demonstrate that the proposed hybrid deep learning-based sentiment analysis model performed better than the previous ones by utilizing additional information from user reviews/comments data with better feature extraction and classification. In the future, sentiment analysis and evaluation are necessary to confirm its superiority and applicability in real-world scenarios, particularly across different cultures.

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REFERENCES

- [1] M. A. Kausar, S. O. Fageeri, and A. Soosaimanickam, "Sentiment Classification based on Machine Learning Approaches in Amazon Product Reviews," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 10849–10855, Jun. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5854>.
- [2] M. R. R. Rana, S. U. Rehman, A. Nawaz, T. Ali, and M. Ahmed, "A conceptual model for decision support systems using aspect based sentiment analysis," *Proceedings of the Romanian Academy*, vol. 22, no. 4, pp. 371–380, Apr. 2021.
- [3] D. Elangovan and V. Subedha, "Adaptive Particle Grey Wolf Optimizer with Deep Learning-based Sentiment Analysis on Online Product Reviews," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 10989–10993, Jun. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5787>.
- [4] P. Resnick and H. R. Varian, "Recommender systems," *Communications of the ACM*, vol. 40, no. 3, pp. 56–59, Mar. 1997.
- [5] D. Jannach, A. Manzoor, W. Cai, and L. Chen, "A Survey on Conversational Recommender Systems," *ACM Computing Surveys*, vol. 54, no. 5, Feb. 2021, Art. no. 105, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3453154>.
- [6] A. Nawaz, T. Ali, Y. Hafeez, S. ur Rehman, and M. R. Rashid, "Mining public opinion: a sentiment based forecasting for democratic elections of Pakistan," *Spatial Information Research*, vol. 30, no. 1, pp. 169–181, Feb. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41324-021-00420-7>.
- [7] M. Mahyoob, J. Algaraady, M. Alrahiali, and A. Alblwi, "Sentiment Analysis of Public Tweets Towards the Emergence of SARS-CoV-2 Omicron Variant: A Social Media Analytics Framework," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 8525–8531, Jun. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4865>.
- [8] W. M. S. Yafooz, E. A. Hizam, and W. A. Alromema, "Arabic Sentiment Analysis on Chewing Khat Leaves using Machine Learning and Ensemble Methods," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 6845–6848, Apr. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4026>.
- [9] H. Wu, Z. Zhang, S. Shi, Q. Wu, and H. Song, "Phrase dependency relational graph attention network for Aspect-based Sentiment Analysis," *Knowledge-Based Systems*, vol. 236, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 107736, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.knsys.2021.107736>.
- [10] A. I. Saad, "Opinion Mining on US Airline Twitter Data Using Machine Learning Techniques," in *2020 16th International Computer Engineering Conference (ICENCO)*, Cairo, Egypt, Sep. 2020, pp. 59–63, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICENCO49778.2020.9357390>.
- [11] M. A. Ullah, S. M. Marium, S. A. Begum, and N. S. Dipa, "An algorithm and method for sentiment analysis using the text and emoticon," *ICT Express*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 357–360, Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.icte.2020.07.003>.
- [12] N. K. Gondhi, U. Chaahat, E. Sharma, A. H. Alharbi, R. Verma, and M. A. Shah, "Efficient Long Short-Term Memory-Based Sentiment Analysis of E-Commerce Reviews," *Computational Intelligence and Neuroscience*, vol. 2022, Jun. 2022, Art. no. e3464524, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/3464524>.
- [13] J. S. Vimali and S. Murugan, "A Text Based Sentiment Analysis Model using Bi-directional LSTM Networks," in *2021 6th International Conference on Communication and Electronics Systems (ICCES)*, Coimbatre, India, Jul. 2021, pp. 1652–1658, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCES51350.2021.9489129>.
- [14] R. Hegde and S. Seema, "Nearest neighbour-based feature selection and classification approach for analysing sentiments," *International Journal of Bioinformatics Research and Applications*, vol. 18, no. 1–2, pp. 16–29, Jan. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJBRA.2022.121757>.
- [15] K. Dhola and M. Saradva, "A Comparative Evaluation of Traditional Machine Learning and Deep Learning Classification Techniques for Sentiment Analysis," in *2021 11th International Conference on Cloud Computing, Data Science & Engineering (Confluence)*, Jan. 2021, pp. 932–936, <https://doi.org/10.1109/Confluence51648.2021.9377070>.
- [16] R. Vatambeti, S. V. Mantena, K. V. D. Kiran, M. Manohar, and C. Manjunath, "Twitter sentiment analysis on online food services based on elephant herd optimization with hybrid deep learning technique," *Cluster Computing*, Feb. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10586-023-03970-7>.
- [17] L. Wang, W. Guo, X. Yao, Y. Zhang, and J. Yang, "Multimodal Event-Aware Network for Sentiment Analysis in Tourism," *IEEE MultiMedia*, vol. 28, no. 2, pp. 49–58, Apr. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MMUL.2021.3079195>.
- [18] F. Huang, X. Zhang, Z. Zhao, J. Xu, and Z. Li, "Image-text sentiment analysis via deep multimodal attentive fusion," *Knowledge-Based Systems*, vol. 167, pp. 26–37, Mar. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.knsys.2019.01.019>.
- [19] J. Xu, Z. Li, F. Huang, C. Li, and P. S. Yu, "Social Image Sentiment Analysis by Exploiting Multimodal Content and Heterogeneous Relations," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 2974–2982, Apr. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TII.2020.3005405>.
- [20] A. Banjar, Z. Ahmed, A. Daud, R. Abbasi, and H. Dawood, "Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis for Polarity Estimation of Customer Reviews on Twitter," *Computers, Materials & Continua*, vol. 67, no. 2, pp. 2203–2225, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.32604/cmc.2021.014226>.
- [21] W. Li, S. Yin, and T. Pu, "Lexical attention and aspect-oriented graph convolutional networks for aspect-based sentiment analysis," *Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems*, vol. 42, no. 3, pp. 1643–1654, Jan. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.3233/JIFS-211045>.
- [22] R. Kora and A. Mohammed, "An enhanced approach for sentiment analysis based on meta-ensemble deep learning," *Social Network Analysis and Mining*, vol. 13, no. 1, Mar. 2023, Art. no. 38, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13278-023-01043-6>.
- [23] A. Nawaz, A. A. Awan, T. Ali, and M. R. R. Rana, "Product's behaviour recommendations using free text: an aspect based sentiment analysis approach," *Cluster Computing*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 1267–1279, Jun. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10586-019-02995-1>.
- [24] R. Catelli, S. Pelosi, and M. Esposito, "Lexicon-Based vs. Bert-Based Sentiment Analysis: A Comparative Study in Italian," *Electronics*, vol. 11, no. 3, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 374, <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics11030374>.
- [25] C. D. Santos and B. Zadrozny, "Learning Character-level Representations for Part-of-Speech Tagging," in *Proceedings of the 31st International Conference on Machine Learning*, Beijing, China, Jun. 2014, pp. 1818–1826.
- [26] X. Wu, "A Dropout Optimization Algorithm to Prevent Overfitting in Machine Learning," *Machine Learning Theory and Practice*, vol. 4, no. 1, Mar. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.38007/ML.2023.040103>.
- [27] H. Xia, Y. Yang, X. Pan, Z. Zhang, and W. An, "Sentiment analysis for online reviews using conditional random fields and support vector machines," *Electronic Commerce Research*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 343–360, Jun. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10660-019-09354-7>.

- [28] Z. Gao, Z. Li, J. Luo, and X. Li, "Short Text Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis Based on CNN + BiGRU," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 12, no. 5, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 2707, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12052707>.
- [29] M. Hu and B. Liu, "Mining and summarizing customer reviews," in *Proceedings of the tenth ACM SIGKDD international conference on Knowledge discovery and data mining*, Seattle, WA, USA, May 2004, pp. 168–177, <https://doi.org/10.1145/1014052.1014073>.
- [30] Md. H. Alam, W.-J. Ryu, and S. Lee, "Joint multi-grain topic sentiment: modeling semantic aspects for online reviews," *Information Sciences*, vol. 339, pp. 206–223, Apr. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2016.01.013>.
- [31] A. L. Maas, R. E. Daly, P. T. Pham, D. Huang, A. Y. Ng, and C. Potts, "Learning word vectors for sentiment analysis," in *Proceedings of the 49th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies - Volume 1*, Portland, OR, USA, Mar. 2011, pp. 142–150.
- [32] Y. Sharma, G. Agrawal, P. Jain, and T. Kumar, "Vector representation of words for sentiment analysis using GloVe," in *2017 International Conference on Intelligent Communication and Computational Techniques (ICCT)*, Jaipur, India, Sep. 2017, pp. 279–284, <https://doi.org/10.1109/INTELCCT.2017.8324059>.
- [33] P. F. Muhammad, R. Kusumaningrum, and A. Wibowo, "Sentiment Analysis Using Word2vec And Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) For Indonesian Hotel Reviews," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 179, pp. 728–735, Jan. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2021.01.061>.
- [34] A. Zhao and Y. Yu, "Knowledge-enabled BERT for aspect-based sentiment analysis," *Knowledge-Based Systems*, vol. 227, Sep. 2021, Art. no. 107220, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.knosys.2021.107220>.
- [35] H. Zhao, Z. Liu, X. Yao, and Q. Yang, "A machine learning-based sentiment analysis of online product reviews with a novel term weighting and feature selection approach," *Information Processing & Management*, vol. 58, no. 5, Sep. 2021, Art. no. 102656, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ipm.2021.102656>.
- [36] M. Rizwan *et al.*, "Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis for Social Multimedia: A Hybrid Computational Framework," *Computer Systems Science and Engineering*, vol. 46, no. 2, pp. 2415–2428, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.32604/csse.2023.035149>.
- [37] J. Mutinda, W. Mwangi, and G. Okeyo, "Sentiment Analysis of Text Reviews Using Lexicon-Enhanced Bert Embedding (LeBERT) Model with Convolutional Neural Network," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 13, no. 3, Jan. 2023, Art. no. 1445, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13031445>.

Mayfly Optimization with Deep Learning-based Robust Object Detection and Classification on Surveillance Videos

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ABSTRACT

Surveillance videos are recordings captured by video recording devices for monitoring and securing an area or property. These videos are frequently used in applications, involving law enforcement, security systems, retail analytics, and traffic monitoring. Surveillance videos can provide valuable visual information for analyzing patterns, identifying individuals or objects of interest, and detecting and investigating incidents. Object detection and classification on video surveillance involves the usage of computer vision techniques to identify and categorize objects within the video footage. Object detection algorithms are employed to locate and identify objects within each frame. These algorithms use various techniques, namely bounding box regression, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), and feature extraction to detect objects of interest. This study presents the Mayfly Optimization with Deep Learning-based Robust Object Detection and Classification (MFODL-RODC) method on surveillance videos. The main aim of the MFODL-RODC technique lies in the accurate classification and recognition of objects in surveillance videos. To accomplish this, the MFODL-RODC method follows a two-step process, consisting of object detection and object classification. The MFODL-RODC method uses the EfficientDet object detector for the object detection process. Besides, the classification of detected objects takes place using the Variational Autoencoder (VAE) model. The MFO algorithm is employed to enrich the performance of the VAE model. The simulation examination of the MFODL-RODC technique is performed on benchmark datasets. The extensive results accentuated the improved performance of the MFODL-RODC method over other existing algorithms with an output of 98.89%.

Keywords-surveillance videos; object detection; deep learning; classification; computer vision

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of surveillance cameras, also known as Closed-Circuit Television (CCTV), has met a fast development in a global scale. The surveillance systems rely on human supervisors who find some practical activities in video scenes. Monitoring parallel events in surveillance displays is complicated and has constraints [2]. Visual surveillance systems can support detecting and tracking objects with several cameras [3]. An advanced surveillance system includes video and image data acquisition devices, data processing - storage devices, and analysis modules, components which are important for the workflow of the system [4]. Due to the latest advances in Deep Learning (DL) based algorithms, Object Detection (OD) has seen considerable progress during the last few decades [5]. Numerous researchers have explored OD by considering every frame of video as an image for detecting objects in videos. But humans do not observe all the frames as

a self-sufficient image in the process of identifying the objects in videos, instead of tracking a movement concerning a prior frame [6]. Hence, video detection techniques like automotive driving, video surveillance, and intelligent robotics are a combination of object tracking and OD techniques. OD is a standard application in Computer Vision (CV) [7]. The task of identifying objects inside the provided images consists of two wide-ranging parts namely object classification and OD [8], with the latter being far more complex. Furthermore, object classification does not work on images that include multiple objects. The DL techniques are utilized for OD for many reasons [9]. DL algorithms are simpler to use and have improved scalability than traditional ML techniques and their capability for processing the data in their raw forms. Besides, DL algorithms are proficient to learn highly complex features by taking the benefits of various levels of representation [10].

This study presents the Mayfly Optimization with Deep Learning based Robust Object Detection and Classification (MFODL-RODC) method. The main aim of the MFODL-RODC technique lies in the accurate classification and recognition of objects in surveillance videos. To accomplish this, the MFODL-RODC method follows a two-step process: object detection and object classification. The MFODL-RODC method uses the EfficientDet object detector for the object detection process. The classification of detected objects takes place using the Variational Autoencoder (VAE) model. The MFO algorithm is employed to enrich the performance of the VAE model. The simulation validation of the MFODL-RODC technique is performed on benchmark datasets.

II. RELATED WORKS

Authors in [11] suggested a new Computational Intelligence-based HSA for Real-Time OD and Tracking (CIHSART-ODT) method on video surveillance systems. The proposed method focuses largely on tracking and detecting the objects that occur in video clippings. Furthermore, the hyperparameter value of the enhanced RefineDet method is finetuned by implementing the Adagrad optimization model. In addition, an HSA with a Twin SVM (TWSVM) algorithm is used for classifying objects. In [12], a CNN is used for enhancing the effectiveness of OD using a Probabilistic Neural Network (PNN) during the evaluation of the images of surveillance videos. Then, the research makes an effort to analyze the essential theories and principles of perceptual and neural networks that are normally left out. Authors in [13] presented the Multi-Object Detection and Tracking (MODT) method. This technique exploits a Kalman filtering model in order to track the objects shifting in video captions which are converted into morphological operations by employing the region-growing method. Kalman filtering is applied after distinguishing the objects, for parameter optimization by implementing a probability-based grasshopper model. Authors in [14] suggested a precise and fast technique for OD. The transfer learning of an effective pre-trained model to a suitable dataset for its applications was suggested. Fine tuning on these pre-trained models was implemented by running backpropagation and replacing the softmax layer. In [15], the authors introduced a new hybridization of ANN in addition to the Oppositional Gravitational Search Optimization (ANN-OGSO) technique based Moving Vehicle Detection (MVD) model. The presented technique comprises two different stages, i.e. vehicle detection and background generation. Initially, an efficient method was introduced for generating the background. Then, the moving vehicles were detected with the ANN-OGSA algorithm. In [16], a new Background Modeling mechanism was developed by using the Biased Illumination Field FCM algorithm for more accurate detection of moving objects. The non-stationary pixels were separated from the stationary via background elimination. Later, the biased illumination field FCM method was used for improving the segmentation performance by clustering under noise and changing illumination environments. Authors in [17] introduced a new architecture which integrates enhanced GMM with postprocessing for the OD process. In this work, pre-processing and post-processing of videos were taken as extrinsic improvements. GMM with parameter initialization was taken

as an essential enhancement. The incorporation of the morphological function with GMM assists segmentation and enhances detection accuracy by decreasing the false positives.

III. THE PROPOSED MODEL

In this study, the novel MFODL-RODC approach for effective object recognition in surveillance videos is introduced. The purpose of the MFODL-RODC approach lies in the accurate classification and detection of objects in surveillance videos. To accomplish this, the MFODL-RODC method follows a two-step process consisting of the EfficientDet-based object detection and MFO with VAE-based object classification. Figure 1 demonstrates the overall flow of the MFODL-RODC algorithm. The suggested technique is put under simulation by employing Python 3.6.5 tool on a PC i5-8600k, 250GB SSD, GeForce 1050Ti 4GB, 16GB RAM, and 1TB HDD. The parameter set up is: learning rate: 0.01, activation: ReLU, epoch count: 50, dropout: 0.5, and batch size: 5.

A. Stage I: Object Detection

In the initial phase, the EfficientDet architecture is utilized. EfficientDet is an OD model that uses optimization and backbone tweaks, such as the use of BiFPN, and a compound scale model that homogeneously scales the width, depth, and resolution of the feature network and class or box prediction network simultaneously [18]. First, the EfficientDet is exploited as a backbone network, later the recurrent BiFPN acts as a feature extraction model for making multiscale feature fusion of P3-P7 features from the EfficientNet. Lastly, the fused features are fed into the box and class predictive network for classification and bounding box prediction. The input can be taken as a low-dimensional compressed representation that is extended to a high dimension by a 1×1 convolutional layer. The feature is filtered with the depth-wise separable convolution for spatial data encoding.

Fig. 1. Overall flow of the MFODL-RODC model.

The SE block employs average pooling for squeezing the spatial data. The aggregated features are set to excitation operators for fully capturing channel-wise dependency. The output features are regarded as a weight of all the channels. Finally, the features are connected to the initial inputs with a reversed residual model for weighting the channels. BiFPN makes various optimizations on Path Aggregation Network (PANet) for further fusing high-level factors in the simplify bi-directional network. Furthermore, all the inputs are added with a further weight such that the network can learn the feature involvement at multiple resolution scales. The final BiFPN enables effective multiscale feature fusion by incorporating weighted feature fusion and bi-directional cross-scale connection. The compound scaling method is proposed due to its accuracy and efficiency. Depth, width, and resolution of the images are scaled-up together by a Φ coefficient, whereby the resource used can be calculated.

B. Object Classification

Once the objects are detected, the process of classification is achieved by employing the VAE technique. A VAE comprises of the encoded network $f_{\phi}^{enc} : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{Z}$ and the decoded network $f_{\theta}^{dec} : \mathcal{Z} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}$, where \mathcal{X} implies the input variable (object) and \mathcal{Z} represents the hidden object domain z [19]. In VAE, input objects x and hidden parameters z are assumed to have arbitrary variables. Let's assume that $p_{\theta}(\mathcal{X})$ and $p_{\theta}(\mathcal{Z})$ are the x and z 's probability functions, correspondingly, where θ denotes the group of parameters for illustrating the probability. The encoded network f_{ϕ}^{enc} is expressed as a conditional probability $q_{\phi}(\mathcal{Z}|\mathcal{X})$ that is assumed as an approximation of $p_{\theta}(\mathcal{Z}|\mathcal{X})$. The decoded network f_{θ}^{dec} and ϕ are expressed as the conditional probability $p_{\theta}(\mathcal{X}|\mathcal{Z})$ and the encoded parameters:

$$J_{VAE}(\phi, \theta) = E_{z \sim q_{\phi}(z|x)} \log p_{\theta}(x|z) - \beta D_{KL}(q_{\phi}(z|x) || p_{\theta}(z)) \quad (1)$$

In VAE, the input or the hidden parameters are assumed as having arbitrary variables. The purpose of VAE training is to maximize a main function which comprises 2 terms: (i) Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence, (ii) reconstruction. The first term inspires the encoding for producing hidden objects that follow past distribution, and the second term makes sure that the input objects are reconstructed in the hidden variable. The VAE main function decreases to objective functions of the typical VAEs once the hyperparameter β is fixed to 1. VAEs with $\beta \neq 1$ are termed as β -VAEs. Figure 2 represents the infrastructure of VAE.

To improve the detection rate of the VAE model, the MFO algorithm is employed. MFO is a robust hybrid optimization technique inspired by the behaviors of MFS in mating. It implements and enhances the global searching of PSO [20]. This technique disregards the lifetime of MFs and in its place considers an adult directly after hatching while only the stronger one survives. A set of male and as female MFS are arbitrarily created. The location vector $P = [p_1, p_2, \dots, p_{d_{Max}}]^T$ signifies the search space, and the agents that perform the search are seeded at first. The main function (OF) estimates the efficiency of the location vector (x). With the velocity vector,

the MFs location is studied considering the revised movement path that can be informed by the individual and social movement experience $K = [k_1, k_2, \dots, k_{d_{Max}}]^T$. Based on its present optimal location, MF moves up or down the search graph.

Fig. 2. Framework of VAE.

A male MF's status can be revised by:

$$p_m(t + 1) = k_m(t + 1) + p_m(t) \quad (2)$$

For the i^{th} MF, $p_m(t)$ denotes the existing position and $p_m(0)$ falls among x_{Min} and x_{Max} . The subsequent time step's MFs position and velocity are denoted by $p_m(t + 1)$ and $k_m(t + 1)$, respectively.

The constant speed is evaluated with the male MFs nuptial dance occurring in a certain height.

$$k_{md}(t + 1) = v_{md}(t) + q_1 \times \exp(-\zeta^{D_p^2}) \times (pbest_{md} - p_{md}(t)) + q_2 \times \exp(-\zeta^{D_g^2}) \times (gbest_d - p_{md}(t)) \quad (3)$$

where q_1 and q_2 indicate the attractive constants that determine the comparative significance of the mental and social elements. MFs cannot see one another very well once they are in a σ environment. Based on (5) and (6), we could define the D_p and D_g distances that p_i has with $pbest_m$ and $gbest$, correspondingly. The i^{th} agent velocity from the d^{th} dimension is represented as k_{md} , while its location can be represented as p_{md} . d shows the dimension index ranges from 1 to d_{Max} , which is the maximum number of dimensions. The optimum location $pbest$ is apprehended by the i^{th} agent at the d^{th} dimension and is evaluated by (4). The quality-defining OF for these solutions is shown as $f(\cdot)$:

$$pbest_m = \begin{cases} x_m(t + 1), f(x_m(t + 1)) < f(pbest_m) \\ pbest_m, f(x_m(t + 1)) \geq f(pbest_m) \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$D_p^2 = (\sum_{n=1}^{d_{Max}} (p_{md} - pbest_m))^0.5 \quad (5)$$

$$D_g^2 = (\sum_{d=1}^{d_{Max}} (p_{md} - gbest))^0.5 \quad (6)$$

$$k_{md}(t + 1) = k_{md}(t) + ND \times \varpi \quad (7)$$

In (7), ND denotes the nuptial dance coefficient and co indicates an arbitrary integer within $[-1, 1]$.

Female MFs do not swarm like males do. Instead, they head straight to the males for mating. Utilizing $r_m(t)$, it is understood that the i^{th} female MF is placed in the searching space after utilizing (8) for adjusting place:

$$r_m(t + 1) = k_m(t + 1) + r_m(t) \tag{8}$$

For modeling this phenomenon, it can be considered that one attractive female can be drawn to one attractive males, after another attractive female is attracted to the next most attractive male, etc. The below equation depicts the speed:

$$k_{md}(t + 1) = \begin{cases} k_{md}(t) + q_2 \times \exp(-\zeta_f^{D_f^2}) \times (p_{md}(t) - r_{md}(t)) \\ f(r_m) > f(p_m) \\ u_{md}(t) + q_w \times \omega, f(r_m) \leq f(p_m) \end{cases} \tag{9}$$

$r_{md}(t)$ and $u_{md}(t)$ define the place and velocity of the i^{th} female MF from the d^{th} dimension at time t , correspondingly. Male and female MFs separate distances are represented by D_{if}^2 . The coefficient of walking, q_w , is selected arbitrarily.

The crossover operator is utilized for modeling the MF mating performance defined as one male and one female can be chosen in all the sets as parents, while males can be attracted to particular females. The selection depends on both chance and the main function. With the employment of the subsequent formulas, the offspring of crossover is predicted:

$$\alpha 1 = \beta \times male + (1 - \beta) \times female \tag{10}$$

$$\alpha 2 = \beta \times female + (1 - \beta) \times male \tag{11}$$

The first two generations of this family are represented by $\alpha 1$ and $\alpha 2$. β'' refers to an arbitrary number in a certain interval. *Male* and *female* signify the biological parents. Fitness choice is a vital feature of the MFO system. An encoding solution was employed to process the better candidate result. Presently, the value of accuracy is the major condition employed to plan a FF.

$$Fitness = \max(P) \tag{12}$$

$$P = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \tag{13}$$

FP and TP represent the false and true positive values.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the object recognition and classification outputs of the MFODL-RODC technique are tested on the UCSDPed2 dataset [21] comprising of 360 frames as portrayed in Table I.

TABLE I. DATASET DESCRIPTION

Dataset	Test dataset	Frame number	Time (s)
UCSDped2	Pedestrian1	360	12
	Pedestrian2		

Figures 3 and 4 depict instances, and the initial and recognized images. Table II represents the average accuracy study of the MFODL-RODC method with other approaches [11, 22-24]. The outcomes show that the MFODL-RODC method has improved performance in comparison with object

detectors with maximum accuracy of 98.89% and 96.23% on SPed-1 and SPed-2 datasets, respectively. The comparative AUC results of the MFODL-RODC technique on two datasets are given in Table III. The outputs imply that the MP-PCA, SF, and SFMP-PCA techniques gave worse results with minimal AUC values.

TABLE II. COMPARISON OF THE AVERAGE ACCURACY OF MFODL-RODC WITH OTHER APPROACHES

Methods	MFODL-RODC	CIHSART-ODT	DLADT	Region CNN	FR-CNN
Surveillance Ped. - 1	98.89	98.00	97.00	97.00	85.00
Surveillance Ped. - 2	96.23	91.00	90.00	87.00	82.00

Fig. 3. Sample images.

Fig. 4. (a) Original and (b) detected images.

On the other hand, the MDT method exhibited a moderate AUC value. A-MDN, AD-VAE, and CIHSART-ODT methods showed reasonable AUC values. But the MFODL-RODC method showed greater performance with the highest AUC values of 99.28% and 96.07% on SPed-1 and SPed-2 datasets.

TABLE III. AUC OUTPUT COMPARISON

Model	SPed-1	SPed-2
MP-PCA	61.01	69.92
SF	66.74	55.96
SFMP-PCA	67.25	61.33
MDT	82.05	82.99
A-MDN	91.71	91.25
AD-VAE	95.39	92.47
CIHSART-ODT	97.12	93.92
MFODL-RODC	99.28	96.07

In Table IV, the Running Time (RT) comparison of the MFODL-RODC technique with recent models on two datasets is shown. The results illustrate that the MDT and SCLF models have poor performance with maximum RT values. The A-MDN model gave slightly decreased RT. Although the AD-VAE and CIHSART-ODT models have obtained close RT values, the MFODL-RODC technique ensured its supremacy with minimal RT of 1.93s and 2.20s on pedestrian-1 and pedestrian-2 datasets, respectively.

TABLE IV. RT OUTPUT COMPARISON

Model	SPed-1	SPed-2
MDT	20.53	22.88
SCLF	20.01	18.54
A-MDN	11.83	13.04
AD-VAE	3.94	6.09
CIHSART-ODT	2.57	4.04
MFODL-RODC	1.93	2.20

TABLE V. ROC OUTPUT COMPARISON ON SPED-1

ROC	SF	A-MDN	AD-VAE	CIHSART-ODT	MFODL-RODC
10	16.65	24.63	20.99	47.51	49.01
20	31.14	46.03	44.43	70.80	72.85
30	41.86	64.90	67.52	91.16	96.24
40	52.58	74.63	80.31	93.35	94.63
50	61.65	82.55	92.69	95.77	99.29
60	70.51	92.12	95.93	98.58	99.89
70	87.53	99.12	100.40	98.06	99.78
80	88.51	93.43	97.86	98.08	99.65
90	89.89	99.25	97.86	99.69	99.91
100	90.20	95.27	96.76	96.87	99.48

TABLE VI. ROC OUTPUT COMPARISON ON SPED-2

ROC	SF	A-MDN	AD-VAE	CIHSART-ODT	MFODL-RODC
10	19.27	26.64	18.30	28.16	56.07
20	28.75	48.29	29.00	61.50	62.56
30	41.05	57.25	69.70	80.01	82.52
40	55.44	74.39	82.33	93.32	97.16
50	74.39	88.12	88.15	97.69	99.18
60	87.87	93.08	95.35	97.18	99.75
70	98.40	99.06	99.02	97.14	99.70
80	98.65	99.71	99.09	98.59	99.96
90	98.06	98.71	98.42	99.01	99.79
100	98.51	97.79	98.52	100.83	99.89

Tables V and VI shows the comparison of the ROC outputs on the SPed-1 and SPed-2 databases. In SPed-1, the SF and AD-VAE techniques showed poor detection performance, the A-MDN model has slightly improved results, and the CIHSART-ODT model has obtained considerably enhanced

performance. Nevertheless, the MFODL-RODC technique showed efficient output with maximum ROC values. In SPed-2 the SF and AD-VAE approach demonstrated worse detection performance, the A-MDN model resulted in somewhat improved outcome, and the CIHSART-ODT model obtained considerably better performance. However, the MFODL-RODC approach has illustrated effectual results with maximal ROC values. These outcomes ensured the improved accomplishment of the MFODL-RODC approach.

V. CONCLUSION

The novel MFODL-RODC approach for effective object recognition in surveillance videos is introduced in this paper. The purpose of the study lies on the accurate classification and detection of objects in surveillance videos. To accomplish this, the MFODL-RODC technique follows a two-step process, consisting of EfficientDet-based object detection and MFO with VAE-based object classification. The MFO technique is employed to improve the solution of the VAE approach. The simulation validations of the MFODL-RODC approach was conducted on a benchmark database. The results highlighted the enhanced outcome of the MFODL-RODC methodology over other known techniques. In the future, advanced DL models will be used to classify the detected objects. In addition, the computational complexity of the proposed model needs to be examined on large-scale real-time datasets.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Y. Ingle and Y.-G. Kim, "Real-Time Abnormal Object Detection for Video Surveillance in Smart Cities," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 10, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 3862, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22103862>.
- [2] R. K. Tripathi, A. S. Jalal, and S. C. Agrawal, "Abandoned or removed object detection from visual surveillance: a review," *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, vol. 78, no. 6, pp. 7585–7620, Mar. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-018-6472-9>.
- [3] C. Fathy and S. N. Saleh, "Integrating Deep Learning-Based IoT and Fog Computing with Software-Defined Networking for Detecting Weapons in Video Surveillance Systems," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 14, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 5075, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22145075>.
- [4] Mohana and H. R. Aradhya, "Object Detection and Tracking using Deep Learning and Artificial Intelligence for Video Surveillance Applications," *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications (IJACSA)*, vol. 10, no. 12, Jun. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.14569/IJACSA.2019.0101269>.
- [5] N. Funde, P. Paranjape, K. Ram, P. Magde, and M. Dhabu, "Object Detection and Tracking Approaches for Video Surveillance Over Camera Network," in *2019 5th International Conference on Advanced Computing & Communication Systems (ICACCS)*, Coimbatore, India, Mar. 2019, pp. 1171–1176, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICACCS.2019.8728518>.
- [6] S. Khan and L. AlSuwaidan, "Agricultural monitoring system in video surveillance object detection using feature extraction and classification by deep learning techniques," *Computers and Electrical Engineering*, vol. 102, Sep. 2022, Art. no. 108201, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compeleceng.2022.108201>.
- [7] F. Pérez-Hernández, S. Tabik, A. Lamas, R. Olmos, H. Fujita, and F. Herrera, "Object Detection Binary Classifiers methodology based on deep learning to identify small objects handled similarly: Application in video surveillance," *Knowledge-Based Systems*, vol. 194, Apr. 2020, Art. no. 105590, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.knsys.2020.105590>.
- [8] S. Nuanmeesri, "A Hybrid Deep Learning and Optimized Machine Learning Approach for Rose Leaf Disease Classification," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7678–7683, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4455>.

- [9] L. Loyani and D. Machuve, "A Deep Learning-based Mobile Application for Segmenting Tuta Absoluta's Damage on Tomato Plants," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7730–7737, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4355>.
- [10] M. V. Daithankar and S. D. Ruikar, "Analysis of the Wavelet Domain Filtering Approach for Video Super-Resolution," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7477–7482, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4262>.
- [11] M. F. Alotaibi, M. Omri, S. Abdel-Khalek, E. Khalil, and R. F. Mansour, "Computational Intelligence-Based Harmony Search Algorithm for Real-Time Object Detection and Tracking in Video Surveillance Systems," *Mathematics*, vol. 10, no. 5, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 733, <https://doi.org/10.3390/math10050733>.
- [12] B. Dhiyanesh, K. Rajesh Kanna, S. Rajkumar, and R. Radha, "Improved Object Detection in Video Surveillance Using Deep Convolutional Neural Network Learning," in *2021 Fifth International Conference on I-SMAC (IoT in Social, Mobile, Analytics and Cloud) (I-SMAC)*, Palladam, India, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/I-SMAC52330.2021.9640894>.
- [13] M. Elhoseny, "Multi-object Detection and Tracking (MODT) Machine Learning Model for Real-Time Video Surveillance Systems," *Circuits, Systems, and Signal Processing*, vol. 39, no. 2, pp. 611–630, Feb. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00034-019-01234-7>.
- [14] M. Ahmadi, W. Ouarda, and A. M. Alimi, "Efficient and Fast Objects Detection Technique for Intelligent Video Surveillance Using Transfer Learning and Fine-Tuning," *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering*, vol. 45, no. 3, pp. 1421–1433, Mar. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13369-019-03969-6>.
- [15] A. Appathurai, R. Sundarasekar, C. Raja, E. J. Alex, C. A. Palagan, and A. Nithya, "An Efficient Optimal Neural Network-Based Moving Vehicle Detection in Traffic Video Surveillance System," *Circuits, Systems, and Signal Processing*, vol. 39, no. 2, pp. 734–756, Feb. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00034-019-01224-9>.
- [16] S. Kalli, T. Suresh, A. Prasanth, T. Muthumanickam, and K. Mohanram, "An effective motion object detection using adaptive background modeling mechanism in video surveillance system," *Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems*, vol. 41, no. 1, pp. 1777–1789, Jan. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.3233/JIFS-210563>.
- [17] F. Joy and D. V. Vijayakumar, "An improved Gaussian Mixture Model with post-processing for multiple object detection in surveillance video analytics," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering Systems*, vol. 13, no. 8, pp. 653–660, Oct. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.32985/ijeces.13.8.5>.
- [18] Y. Ye *et al.*, "An Adaptive Attention Fusion Mechanism Convolutional Network for Object Detection in Remote Sensing Images," *Remote Sensing*, vol. 14, no. 3, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 516, <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14030516>.
- [19] O. Boyar, K. Iwata, H. Hanada, and I. Takeuchi, "Sample-Efficient De Novo Chemical Design with Latent Reconstruction-Aware Variational Autoencoder," presented at the 37th Annual Conference of the Japanese Society for Artificial Intelligence, Apr. 2023.
- [20] N. Alqahtani *et al.*, "Deep Belief Networks (DBN) with IoT-Based Alzheimer's Disease Detection and Classification," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 13, no. 13, Jan. 2023, Art. no. 7833, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13137833>.
- [21] "UCSD Anomaly Detection Dataset." <http://www.svcl.ucsd.edu/projects/anomaly/dataset.htm>.
- [22] I. V. Pustokhina, D. A. Pustokhin, T. Vaiyapuri, D. Gupta, S. Kumar, and K. Shankar, "An automated deep learning based anomaly detection in pedestrian walkways for vulnerable road users safety," *Safety Science*, vol. 142, Oct. 2021, Art. no. 105356, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2021.105356>.
- [23] M. Xu, X. Yu, D. Chen, C. Wu, and Y. Jiang, "An Efficient Anomaly Detection System for Crowded Scenes Using Variational Autoencoders," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 9, no. 16, Jan. 2019, Art. no. 3337, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app9163337>.
- [24] B. S. Murugan, M. Elhoseny, K. Shankar, and J. Uthayakumar, "Region-based scalable smart system for anomaly detection in pedestrian walkways," *Computers & Electrical Engineering*, vol. 75, pp. 146–160, May 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compeleceng.2019.02.017>.

The Impact of Web Analytics Tools on the Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises

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ABSTRACT

In the era of data analytics, the use of web analytics tools is widely spread among Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), especially in the e-commerce sector, to analyze web usage data and measure website performance due to the several features it provides. Most web analytics studies were conducted based on marketing rather than a managerial point of view. Therefore, there is a necessity to study the impact from a managerial perspective by exploring the impact on financial and non-financial performance and the decision-making process. This study assessed the impact of web analytics tools on the overall performance of SMEs, targeting Saudi SMEs and considering the lack of web analytics studies in this sector in Saudi Arabia. The sample involved eight Saudi SMEs who participated by answering interview questions, which were analyzed using thematic analysis. The findings demonstrated four main themes: the current web analytics tools used by Saudi SMEs, the motivations behind their use, and their impact on SMEs' performance and decision-making. The results showed that these tools positively affect the overall performance of SMEs. Google Analytics (GA) was the tool most used by the sample. Seven motives were discovered that encourage SMEs to use web analytics tools. This study also addressed the common Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) used by the participants. Concerning decision-making, it was found that web analytics tools affected and supported SMEs' decisions. Furthermore, this study evaluated the role of Zid, the Saudi e-commerce platform for data analytics and performance measurement.

Keywords-web analytics tools; SMEs;KPIs; google Analytics; e-commerce; data analytics

I. INTRODUCTION

Until recently, Saudi SMEs relied on social networks to sell their products and services through simple direct messages. However, with the establishment of e-commerce platforms, such as Salla and Zid, most SMEs now have online stores to operate their businesses. These platforms help SMEs to start and grow their businesses online by creating and designing their online stores, managing their inventory, providing different types of digital payments, and delivering marketing solutions. The Saudi government plays an important role in supporting SMEs, as it established Monsha'at in 2016, Saudi Arabia's General Authority for Small and Medium Enterprises, to regulate, support, develop, and sponsor the SME sector. Monsha'at created an academy to provide different online courses in e-commerce, marketing, and supply chain management, to help SMEs gain knowledge in various business areas. The number of SMEs operating in Saudi Arabia increased to 752,560 in the first quarter of 2022, showing a 14.6% increase yearly [1]. To survive in this competitive sector, SMEs have to exploit digital technologies in various areas. Outsourcing information technology support could help

SMEs operating in the e-commerce sector to continue adopting e-commerce technology [2]. Today, SMEs have access to a wide range of e-commerce technologies and data analysis capabilities that facilitate their development journey. Although e-commerce offers a great opportunity to build a competitive advantage over other competitors, the challenge is to what extent they can employ technology to make decisions on a solid basis [3].

In our data-driven world, most decisions are based on data analytics. Data analytics provide huge opportunities for SMEs in production, marketing, and quality control [4]. On the contrary, some obstacles prevent SMEs from adopting advanced data analytics, such as mastering big data analytics and data mining techniques [5]. Previous studies specified these obstacles as weak data infrastructure, limited financial resources, lack of IT skills, lack of analytical expertise, limited business cases, and data security and privacy concerns [6-8]. Based on these obstacles, some SMEs rely entirely on web analytics tools such as GA due to their usability, free cost, and availability of online tutorials. In addition, GA installation does not require technical skills [9]. Web analytics tools enable

enterprises, marketers, web developers, and web designers to attain a great deal of insights. In [10], a set of benefits of web analytics was illustrated: understanding user behavior, generating data on customer demographics and geolocations, identifying new and returning visitors, determining the frequently visited pages, and representing key metrics. In [11], it was stated that understanding how to use web analytics tools is essential for every entrepreneur.

According to [12], there are seven leading e-commerce analytics tools: Kiss metrics, RetentionGrid, Metrilo, Clicky, Adobe Marketing Cloud, GA, and Crazy Egg. GA is a Google marketing platform that provides numerous business and marketing insights for free and is one of the best-known web analytics tools. However, there are monthly paid plans for more advanced features. Web page owners can trace customers' visits and generate data related to their purchasing behavior. Accordingly, they can choose the best method to reach and acquire potential customers and promote their products/services. GA can collect data from different system types, such as customer relationship systems, websites, and mobile applications. This tool helps businesses measure the success of their marketing campaigns, assess the effectiveness of their promotions, and understand the customer journey. As a result, they can view and understand the full picture of their online presence [10].

To the best of our knowledge, there is a lack of research on the impact of web analytics tools on the overall performance of SMEs. Many studies focused on examining the impact of web analytics tools from a marketing perspective [13-16]. In addition, as there is a lack of investigations on the Saudi SME sector, it is necessary to study the impact of web analytics tools on the overall performance of Saudi SMEs. Saudi SMEs and e-commerce platforms rely on web analytics tools more than on big data analytics to analyze web usage data due to the various barriers to the use of the latter. Therefore, it is necessary to understand the current situation and investigate how the use of web analytics impacts the performance of Saudi SMEs. This study aimed to investigate the impact of web analytics tools on the overall performance of SMEs in Saudi Arabia. The research objectives were to understand the current use of web analytics tools in Saudi SMEs, identify the reasons for their use, and investigate whether web analytics tools have a positive or negative impact on their overall performance. Overall, this study extends previous web analytics studies by providing new insights related to their use from a managerial eye.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Web Analytics Overview

Web analytics aims to collect and analyze web usage data and traffic [17]. Web analytics is the technology and method for the collection, measurement, analysis, and reporting of website and web application usage data [18-19]. Web analytics is under the umbrella of web mining, specifically web usage mining [20]. However, web analytics is a descriptive analytics methodology, as it describes web usage data, using different metrics to provide insights about a website and how it is being used, while web mining focuses on identifying previously unknown patterns from Internet data. There are two main

categories of web analytics. Off-site web analytics collect and measure data about an enterprise's online presence outside the website through the audience, electronic Word-Of-Mouth (e-WOM), and buzzwords. On-site web analytics focus on collecting and measuring data about customers' clicks and visitors' behavior. Most web analytics tools apply on-site analytics as they help website owners compare metrics against their Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to generate more insights that can be used in the decision-making process [20].

Web analytics emerged during the evolution of the Internet using web server log files. In 1993, WebTrends was one of the leading commercial software companies that utilized web server logs for data collection and analysis [21]. Log files have some downsides as they do not provide information about the size or resolution of the client's screen, keyboard pressing, or clicking behavior [18]. As a result, page tagging or JavaScript tagging became another method to collect data without using log files. Page tagging works based on JavaScript code embedded in each web page [22]. Page tagging has more features, as it produces clean and reliable data, suitable for analyzing human activities [10]. Using page tagging, it is easy to identify unique visitors through cookies and browser fingerprints. On the other hand, web log analytics is less expensive and suitable for analyzing sensitive and historical data. Although web server logs and page tagging are the two main methods used to capture data, there are more comprehensive methods such as web beacons, event logs, application-level logs, and packet sniffers [18, 23]. Cookies are the most common data collection method used in web analytics [18]. Cookies are small text files embedded in the user's computer, and there are two types: session cookies, which are removed once the visitor leaves the website, and persistent cookies, which remain on the visitor's computer [24]. Furthermore, it is possible to combine two or more data collection methods, depending on the business goal [23].

Fig. 1. Google analytics report dashboard.

Most data produced by on-site web analytics are based on customers' clicks. Reports illustrate data about visitors (total visitors, number of visitors, and unique visitors), page views (individual page views along with some mathematics such as total, average, minimum, and maximum), time (session duration, time spent per visitor), and referrers (keywords, websites, and trends) [23]. The referrer is the URL that originally generated the request for the current page view or object [19]. These are the most important and popular web

analytics metrics used by businesses and marketers. Figure 1 shows an example of a GA dashboard report. However, organizations can use other external data sources, such as surveys, public information on social media, and competitor comparisons [18]. Similarweb is one of the common software companies that specialize in measuring digital traffic and website performance [25]. One of its features is benchmarking, which enables businesses to compare themselves against rivals or compare two different businesses.

B. Web Analytics Tools

Choosing the right and most suitable web analytics tool is a critical process as it influences long-term strategy, particularly in the decision-making process [26]. In [22], the criteria for selecting the correct tool were usability, functionalities, technical details, and total cost. Accordingly, businesses have to submit a Request for Proposal and analyze their needs before selecting a web analytics tool. Globally, several web analytics tools are widely used, such as GA, Yahoo, Hotjar, Adobe Analytics, and Microsoft Advertising.

In 2005, GA was introduced as a free-service Google marketing platform product to track customer journeys and enhance Return On Investment (ROI). GA is the most popular and fastest-growing traffic analysis tool [27]. The ability to integrate with other Google products such as its search engine, AdWords, and Ads Manager, as well as non-Google products, is one of the main features that increased its popularity among SMEs [28]. GA features have been studied in multiple studies [11, 28-29]. In addition, Google offered free GA heat maps that can be installed directly in the Chrome browser, called Page Analytics. Heat maps show the density of customers' clicks on webpages [23]. However, since 2019, it has been blocked for multiple users because Google stopped updating the extension [30]. Hotjar provides two main products to understand customer click behavior: heatmaps and recordings [31]. There are three types of heatmaps: scroll maps, click maps, and move maps, and Figure 2 illustrates the first two. These heatmaps can be integrated with GA for effective results. Given the increasing use of free web analytics tools such as GA, in [26] it was proclaimed that these tools are useful for enterprises with a low number of visitors, but they could result in a low business improvement for those who already have a large number of visitors.

Fig. 2. A Hotjar scroll map and click map.

C. The Use of Web Analytics by SMEs

SMEs are highly supported by the Saudi government due to their power in the economy. In Saudi Arabia, two major e-

commerce companies help SMEs build and operate their websites: Salla and Zid. Zid Analytics supports three major web analytics tools: GA, Hotjar, and Crazyegg, and all these tools can be integrated with SMEs' online stores. Figure 3 shows the web analytics tools that are listed in the Zid application store. In [26], a comparison framework was developed, showing that an enterprise's size influences its selection of web analytics tools. GA is the most popular web analytics tool among SMEs. In [32], an ontology model was proposed that aimed to integrate web analytics data into e-commerce. From a sample of 150 SMEs, 68% of e-commerce SMEs used GA to analyze their web data. Web analytics can provide great benefits to SMEs. In [33], it was stated that integrating the technical perspective of Web log analytics with a business/marketing perspective can highlight not just what insights can be gained, but how they can be used to guide effective decision-making about the specific website.

Fig. 3. Zid application store.

D. Web Analytics Tools and Performance of SMEs

Today, financial metrics are no longer enough to measure the performance of companies, as SMEs need to employ a combination of financial and non-financial indicators to assess their performance, and there is a complexity in measuring non-financial indicators [34]. For e-commerce enterprises, web analytics tools provide a way of measuring non-financial indicators by tracking website data, enabling SMEs to understand their online presence. Web analytics metrics and KPIs play a role in measuring website performance. Web analytics is the foundation of a performance-driven website [35]. To set the correct web metrics and KPIs, companies must identify their business goals and objectives. In [29], the importance of aligning KPIs with the business strategy was addressed, a framework was provided to help SMEs make better use of web analytics, and it was shown that identifying KPIs based on the type of website is an efficient method for SMEs. The most common KPIs used by commerce websites are Conversion Rates (CR), Average Order Value (AOR), customer loyalty, and bounce rate [21]. For example, in e-commerce, if an SME's business goal is to increase its customer base, it has to focus on a certain performance indicator, conversion rate. The conversion rate is calculated by taking the number of conversions and dividing it by the total number of ad interactions [36]. To achieve this goal, it is also important to reduce bounce rate and assess the reasons why customers leave the site without making a single transaction [37].

The Zid platform provides another service called Qumra, which is an application that provides all the detailed performance indicators for the stores operating under it and financial metrics such as total cash on delivery, service charges, vouchers, and total value-added tax. Figure 4 shows all the performance indicators measured by Qumra, which offers different subscription plans at affordable prices and is flexible to use [38].

Fig. 4. Qumra application services.

To conclude, big and small enterprises have started to invest their time and money in web analytics due to its effectiveness. There is a positive correlation between usage frequency and user satisfaction with a web analytics tool, based on each activity: measuring, collecting, analyzing, and reporting [22]. SMEs must also be aware of the importance of data-driven decision-making. Lastly, SMEs must keep up to date with digital changes by exploring trends and opportunities that will allow them to become more competitive and innovative in the market [39].

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

According to [40], there are eight well-known qualitative research approaches. This study investigated the impact of web analytics tools on SMEs' performance in Saudi Arabia by adopting an interpretive qualitative approach, aiming to understand in detail how the participants view web analytics tools and performance. In Saudi Arabia, the SME board defines SMEs based on two factors: the number of employees and revenue. Small enterprises consist of 6 to 49 employees or revenue of 3 to less than 40 million riyals (from \$799.9K to less than \$10.7M), while medium enterprises consist of 50 to 249 employees or revenue ranging from 40 to 200 million riyals (\$10.7-53.3M) [41]. The study sample was selected with these factors in mind. Accordingly, the target sample was Saudi SMEs that used web analytics tools to analyze their web usage data, and these were chosen from LinkedIn, Instagram, and WhatsApp accounts. To accomplish the research goal, semi-structured in-depth interviews were conducted with some Saudi SMEs, aiming to generate focused findings. The interviews began at the end of December 2022, and each audio file was transcribed to be ready for the analysis phase. During the interviews, the interviewer managed and controlled the discussion to keep it within the scope of the investigation. Most of the questions were open-ended, so they provided the participants with the opportunity to elaborate. Additionally,

follow-up and extension questions were asked to generate in-depth explanations and insights. All interviews were conducted online due to the difference in the geographic locations of researchers and participants. The participants were eight employees from different SMEs. Replication was the main criterion for identifying the maximum number of interviewees required [42]. Furthermore, the positions of the participants depended on the size of the SMEs. In small enterprises, owners were interviewed, while in medium enterprises, the e-commerce manager, digital marketing expert, and online store manager were interviewed, as shown in Table I.

TABLE I. INTERVIEW OVERVIEW

Interview no.	Independent company	Participant position	e-commerce platform	Enterprise size
1	No	Digital marketing experts & store manager	Salla	Medium
2	Yes	Owner	Zid	Small
3	Yes	Owner	Zid	Small
4	Yes	Co-founder	Zid	Small
5	Yes	Owner	Zid	Medium
6	Yes	Vice president	Zid	Small
7	Yes	Owner	Zid	Small
8	Yes	E-commerce manager	Zid	Medium

The names of the participants were kept secret for ethical considerations. A consent form was provided to each interviewee in Arabic and English. The form specified the researcher's name, research topic, and aim. The data collection procedure was cleared to ensure the privacy of the participants.

To derive substantive insights from the interviews, thematic analysis was considered the most appropriate methodology to employ. Thematic analysis is defined as a method for systematically identifying, organizing, and offering insight into the patterns of meaning/themes across a data set [43]. To ensure that the interview questions reflected the research objectives, the first interview was conducted as a pilot with a participant from the same research sample. The data generated from the interviews was in verbal form. Voice-recognition software was used for transcription. Since the participants were employees of Saudi SMEs, most of the interviews took place in Arabic. Therefore, all the transcripts were translated into English, using Microsoft Word to code and analyze the data. The codes were combined into different categories based on their similarities. Then, the main theme and subthemes were generated from these categories. Lastly, the findings were reached. Both authors agreed on the main themes after coding each interview individually and discussing the derived categories, themes, and sub-themes.

IV. RESULTS

The findings showed that web analytics tools positively affect the overall performance of Saudi SMEs within the e-commerce sector, particularly in three major pillars: financial performance, nonfinancial performance, and the decision-making process. Products, customers, advertising, and delivery aspects fall within the category of nonfinancial performance. In response to the question "From your experience, do web analytics tools have a positive or negative impact on the overall

performance and how?", One participant said: "Significantly positive. Because without these tools it will take a lot of time and effort to reach our target customers. Also, we might target the wrong customers. But, with these tools, it will be easy to reach our target customers" (Participant #3).

At first, the current situation was determined regarding which web analytics tools were used by the sample. Then, the reasons that motivated them to use these tools were identified. After that, the impact of the web analytics tools on financial, non-financial performance, and decision-making was analyzed. Four main themes were derived from the data: web analytics tools used by SMEs, SMEs' motivations, SMEs' performance, and the decision-making process. Each theme reflects one of the research objectives, as shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Research result themes.

A. Web Analytics Tools Used by SMEs

The research findings identified the three most major and frequently used web analytics tools among the participants: GA, Zid Analytics and Qumra, and Hotjar. Each tool offers a set of features or characteristics.

1) Google Analytics

Although all participants used GA to analyze and measure their web usage data, they did it in different ways. Some of the participants depended entirely on GA to measure performance, while some diversified their web analytics tools using Hotjar or Zid and Qumra analytical dashboards along with GA. Four of the participants agreed that GA provided more comprehensive web analytics metrics than other tools. For instance, "For more accurate and comprehensive metrics, we use Google Analytics" (Participant #3), and "Google Analytics is more general and provides us with a big picture" (Participant #6). All participants stated that GA provides accurate results. The first participant indicated the difference between the new version of GA, which is G4, and the previous one, Universal Analytics (UA): "Google Analytics G4 provides me with more accurate results than UA". On the other hand, Participant #8 said: "Google Analytics provides a close and accurate result of 95-96%".

In terms of performance, one of the participants indicated the importance of GA: "The performance indicators produced by GA are one of the main things that help us reach our goals, they tell us where we are going. What are the things we need to focus more on? What are the points we need to learn from?

What should we specialize in or be distinguished to benefit from them? It serves as a reference for us" (Participant #3).

GA also helped two of the participants identify sales, customers, and campaign problems, solve them, and assess the solutions. "Google Analytics helps me identify the problem related to, for example, a drop in certain page links. We find solutions and solve the problem completely. After one month we assess the solution, and we see a big difference before and after. It helps us improve the website's performance and increase sales in general" (Participant #1).

2) Zid Analytics & Qumra

Seven participants built their websites through Zid and took advantage of the Zid analytical dashboards and reports. Six participants used Qumra, also a Zid product, to measure their performance through several performance indicators. Participants who used both Zid Analytics and Qumra agreed that they were similar in terms of usability. Both tools can be used by any Zid website owner. "Zid is one of the most important companies in Saudi Arabia that provide you with a platform and they support you in the analysis process" (Participant #2). Regarding the Qumra Application, several features were identified by the participants:

- Qumra is simpler than GA: "In Google Analytics, the language of numbers speaks greater, but in Qumra, it may be very simple" (Participant #2).
- Qumra provides limited performance indicators: Qumra provides a list of performance indicators, which were not enough for one of the SMEs. The owner saw that Qumra helped them in specific areas but not all of them: "Up to now, it has not met all the needs of company owners. But it helps us to understand products, for example, we can see which is the best-selling product. It helps us to understand the geographical data related to high AOV. Also, it helps us to answer questions like 'What is the shipping company preferred by our customers?'. These are examples of how Qumra performance indicators help us" (Participant #2).
- Qumra is available at an affordable price: "It has a simple price of forty-nine riyals per month. It is good for those who are looking for quick information" (Participant #2).
- It is easy for non-professional data analysts to use Qumra: "Qumra is unique in terms of targeting those who have the basics and a simple limit of knowledge in terms of data analysis" (Participant #2).

Lastly, only one of the participants who had built their website with Zid declared that the Zid analytical dashboard provided inaccurate results: "The figures that were presented in Zid were inaccurate. We never relied on them. We rely on our work, through internal analysis" (Participant #7).

3) Hotjar

Only three of the participants used the Hotjar web analytics tool, which concentrates on the Heatmap feature for its analysis. In their view, heatmaps helped them design their online stores and understand customer behavior: "There are specific things we checked through Hotjar because it illustrates

a screenshot of customers' behavior on the site, so we know if this button is not clear. This is a page where a specific element needs to be removed, enlarged, reduced, or even added again" (Participant #6), and "It has a very big role, for example, understanding the customer journey. In Hotjar we can know the customers' focus, what they see, and more" (Participant #5).

B. Motivations of SMEs

Participants were asked about their reasons for using web analytics tools. Figure 6 shows the seven motives found to encourage them to continue using these tools to analyze their websites and measure their performance.

Fig. 6. SMEs' seven motives for using web analytics tools.

1) Direction

Four participants agreed that web analytics tools provide direction and guide them in their business growth: "Web analytics tools help us to go further" (Participant #2), "Web analytics tools provide us with daily and monthly performance indicators. Also, they help us to understand whether we are on the right path or not in terms of accomplishing our goals" (Participant #5), and "Web analytics tools are a compass for the online store" (Participant #3).

2) Reach Strategic Goals

Half of the participants stated that web analytics tools help them reach their strategic goals and objectives: "Web analytics metrics show us whether we have reached the target goals or not" (Participant #5), "In the business world, the more we have an accurate and large amount of data, the easier we can reach our goals" (Participant #3), and "In 2022, I used Google Analytics intensely, and frankly, I had a growth in sales of more than thirty to forty percent" (Participant #1).

3) Accelerate Growth

Participants saw that web analytics tools played a role in accelerating their business growth. Business growth is defined by the participants as accomplishing goals, increasing customer

base, increasing sales volume, and product success: "I think the deeper we go into web analytics tools, the more we rely on them, they make a great impression on us, and they give us positive and accurate results. The impression can be the success of the company and maybe the success of the product" (Participant #3), and "Web analytics tools help us to accelerate our reach or speed of growth" (Participant #3).

4) Accurate and Fast Results

Six participants confirmed that web analytics tools provided them with quick and accurate results on web analytics metrics. When discussing this motive, one of the participants likened web analytics tools to a book that consists of historical and real-time data. "The first thing is the speed of measuring results. In the business world, the time when you are late launching a new product, or there is a delay in advertising such a product, many people have been racing you in this matter" (Participant #3), and "Web analytics tools provide a close and accurate result of approximately 95%" (Participant #8).

5) Detecting and Solving Problems

Detecting and solving problems was the most frequently mentioned motive among the participants to use web analytics tools. "Sometimes we see that there is traffic on particular products but not on other products, so we know that there is something wrong, for example in the price, so we adjust the prices or offers" (Participant #4). "Web analytics tools help us to understand the problem. For example, we sometimes see that a product is added to the basket without purchases, then we find that the product description is not clear or incomplete" (Participant #4).

6) Top Management Support

One of the participants declared that top management support plays a role in increasing the use of web analytics tools. Also, he stated that management awareness of web analytics increased after the COVID-19 pandemic and that employers started to know some of the keywords used in web analytics such as CR: "Top management support and awareness increased after COVID-19 related to the use of web analytics tools" and "After the COVID-19 pandemic, the manager became interested, for example, in CR. The development related to analytics is greater than before the pandemic" (Participant #1).

7) Decision-making Support

Web analytics tools supported four of the participants in the decision-making process. One of the participants discovered that customers did not spend more than a specific amount on one basket, so they decided to replace one of their products with an alternative product. For example: "We came down with a product with fewer features and less service. We dropped the price to an average of five hundred or six hundred riyals. It was also seasonal" (Participant #2). "We can't make decisions if there is no data or numbers in front of us. I mean, it's always the numbers that give us clear signals" (Participant #4). "Web analytics tools help us make decisions because they enable us to monitor the website status with full details from A to Z" (Participant #8).

C. SMEs' Performance

The participants were asked about the impact of using web analytics tools on measuring and monitoring performance. Most of the participants were aware of their important role in assessing financial and non-financial areas using several performance indicators. The main theme was divided into three sub-themes: financial performance, nonfinancial performance, and KPIs. "Of course, these web analytics metrics help us to improve and develop the performance in general" (Participant #1). "For us, it gives us great flexibility for the company in its performance at the level of KPIs from the operational side or as an outcome" (Participant #5). In addition, one of the participants clarified that web analytics tools have a greater impact if they are used by professionals or subject experts in SMEs: "We have brought in special people or people who have great experience in this area, and they have helped us greatly. So, number one is: to go to competent people" (Participant #3).

1) Financial Performance

The results showed three major effects of web analytics tools. First, they increase cash flow. For instance, they helped one of the participants identify the right time to advertise and sell seasonal products: "We discovered that people wanted to buy seasonal products before the season, so we added the products before their time. This helps us to dispose of old products and benefit from the cash" (Participant #2). In addition, web analytics tools reduce costs: "We found that the Eastern province prefers Aramex as a shipping company, rather than SMSA, so we canceled the other company to increase the orders and reduce the cost economically" (Participant #2). Furthermore, web analytics tools minimize the possibility of loss. "Instead of consuming a lot of human energy who may succeed with me or not. The technology in this way gives me an accurate, clear, reliable measurement that can be referred to at any time." (Participant #3). In summary, web analytics tools help SMEs manage their resources better.

2) Nonfinancial Performance

Most participants used web analytics non-financial performance indicators to assess or measure their performance in terms of products, delivery, advertisement campaigns, and customer satisfaction. Eleven effects were generated from the interviews and combined based on their similarities into four categories:

a) Products

- Web analytics tools help improve products by facilitating the understanding of several metrics: "Web analytics tools help us to monitor how far the customer accepts the products we offer. What percentage of customers enter the website and conduct a transaction? Well, how many of those who bought return to buy, or send a coupon to a second person to buy our products? It measures the impact of the product in the market" (Participant #8).
- Web analytics tools help sell the right product: "Let's assume that we decided to sell a new product, and we entered the market without relying on analysis tools. If the product is a wrong choice, and the target group is wrong, it

will be a loss, starting from entering the market up to reaching customers" (Participant #3).

- Web analytics tools help select the right time to launch a new product: "In the year 2020, we sold certain products during the summer season. The year after that we did not. Through GA we found that customers were looking for these products before the summer season. It helped us to add these products at a specific time based on customer demand" (Participant #2).
- Web analytics tools help identify products that need more investment: "Sometimes data determine products that we should pay attention to and invest in more, although we did not think that this would achieve results; data can give us another perspective" (Participant #4).
- Web analytics tools help assess product quality: Some of the participants used external web analytic data collection tools like surveys and A/B tests to assess customer experience and product quality. "Surveys were sent to customers to evaluate the quality of the entire experience, including the product, and the delivery service, these help us greatly" (Participant #6).

b) Advertisement

- Web analytics tools help to assess the impact of social media influencers: "In Google Analytics, we can evaluate the advertisers or the influencers who advertise our products. Also, we can evaluate the advertisement channel based on it, and the conversion rate" (Participant #5).
- Web analytics tools help businesses understand advert impressions: "Google Analytics shows you the numbers of visitors currently, especially after ads or huge campaigns, through the entry rate and conversion rate" (Participant #5).

c) Delivery

- Web analytics tools help SMEs discover the locations of high basket value: "We found that some small cities in Saudi Arabia have a high basket value compared to big cities like Riyadh, so we studied why. We discovered that physical stores in small cities are few and far between. So, they order a large number of products with one shipping cost rather than buying one or two products including shipping cost, and repeat ordering more after one month for example. Especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, more of the orders were from small cities such as Jizan" (Participant #2).
- Web analytics tools help businesses identify suitable shipping companies: "Through the analysis, we identified that the eastern province prefers Aramex as a shipping company more than SMSA, so we added a different shipping option" (Participant #2).

d) Customers

- Web analytics tools help SMEs understand customer behavior: "During the World Cup, we made a quick campaign, and the return was more than 2,500 orders. Based on these tools we analyzed our current customers and what they wanted or preferred, so we introduced an offer

(buy one product and get one free)" (Participant #2). "These tools help us understand the customer. For example, through the exit rate within a certain page, we can see that some customers don't like the shipping method or the payment methods, and we act upon that" (Participant #5).

- Web analytics tools help SMEs reach the right target customers: "Web analytics tools help us understand customer behavior, improve customer experience and identify the target customers to reach them in the marketing campaigns" (Participant #6).

3) KPIs

Regarding the use of KPIs, the participants were divided into two categories. Three of the participants did not rely on web analytics KPIs to measure their performance but used sales and ROI to assess their overall performance. Participant #1 said: "We rely on sales by 90%, and the other 10% we focus on customer satisfaction". However, most of the participants realized the importance of KPIs and planned to set their own KPIs that aligned with their strategic goals by the beginning of 2023. One of the main reasons for this is that after the COVID-19 pandemic, top managers became more aware of web analytics tools in general and non-financial performance indicators, such as the CR. However, five participants relied on web analytics KPIs to assess their performance and make decisions. The common KPIs used by the participants were CR, AOV, and retention rate. Other KPIs used were the number of visits, click-through rate, transit time, delivery rate, traffic growth, and total number of orders. Also, financial KPIs were used, such as total sales and ROI.

D. Decision-making Process

Web analytics tools had a great impact on SMEs' decisions. The participants were asked: "How far do web analytics tools impact a company's decision-making?". Six of the eight participants said that web analytics metrics affected their decisions, both day-to-day and long-term. "Web analytics tools results could tell us to stop investing in specific products that do not reach the target sales, so in this situation, we continue to sell the available stock and then we start looking for an alternative product" (Participant #4). "As e-commerce, we can change our decisions on large campaigns based on web analytics tools results, in terms of adjusting prices, modifying discount methods, packaging, and bundling. These are all changed periodically based on the reports. Reports are important to us" (Participant #5). "Web analytics tools affect our decisions by 60%" (Participant #8). Figure 7 presents a Venn diagram of the three main performance pillars that are impacted by the use of web analytics tools in SMEs.

V. DISCUSSION

Based on the findings, it is obvious that Saudi SMEs use web analytics tools in several areas, such as product improvement, problem-solving, decision-making, and goal achievement. However, most of them limit their use to free tools, in particular those oriented toward marketing areas, as these serve their current needs. GA was the main tool used by participants to analyze web usage data, possibly due to enterprise size [26]. Enterprise size plays a role in selecting a

web analytics tool and SMEs are more oriented to free web analytics tools, particularly GA. In addition, the study did not find challenges related to the use of web analytics tools. On the contrary, the participants were satisfied with their frequent use of web analytics tools, as in [22]. Furthermore, the results should encourage SMEs that have not yet used these tools to utilize them to measure and monitor their online store and overall performance. The three main motivators among the participants were achieving strategic goals, detecting and solving problems, and providing direction.

Fig. 7. The impact of web analytics tools on the performance of SMEs.

E-commerce SMEs in Saudi Arabia are growing rapidly, especially since the COVID-19 pandemic. In addition, they have gained a lot of government and private support. This study proved the key role of the Zid e-commerce platform in the SME sector, particularly in terms of web analytics. Although Qumra is a recent application, it has become one of the most important applications for SMEs that use the Zid platform, especially as a convenient measure of performance. Qumra developers need to consider SME reviews to level up the application. The results showed that heatmaps are still not commonly used by Saudi SMEs, despite their benefits in terms of understanding customer behavior. Web analytics metrics and KPIs were the main focus of SMEs, rather than heatmaps.

For measuring performance, the KPIs used were a mix of financial and non-financial performance indicators, providing insight into increased awareness of these types of indicators [34]. Furthermore, the findings demonstrate that they complement each other during the performance measurement process. The selection of KPIs was aligned with the enterprise goals [29] and website type in this research sample of e-commerce websites [21]. The most frequently used performance indicators were CR, AOV, and sales volume. Although increased awareness is related to non-financial performance indicators, some top managers are concerned only about sales and ROI as major indicators. Therefore, it is recommended to expand their knowledge of non-financial indicators, as they have recently become as important as financial indicators. The use of web analytics tools helps SMEs achieve their enterprise goals, supports decision-making, and improves enterprise performance. However, SMEs have to reconsider their use of web analytics tools in the long term,

increase their analytical knowledge, and hire expert analysts to analyze their web data in-house or through more advanced tools. The reason for this suggestion is that free tools are not considered a permanent solution for them and can lead to fewer improvements [26]. Expanding the number of visitors will increase the customer base.

VI. CONCLUSION, IMPLICATIONS, AND FUTURE WORK

This study assessed the effects of web analytics tools on the performance of SMEs in Saudi Arabia by interviewing some SME owners and employees. Thematic analysis was used to analyze the interviews, generating four main themes. Each theme reflected a research objective. At first, the web analytics tools used by the sample were determined. Then, seven motives were identified that encouraged SMEs to use web analytics tools, and finally, the impact of web analytics tools was established on financial and non-financial performance, and decision-making. Along with performance, it was determined that the sample used KPIs frequently. The findings convey that web analytics tools positively affect the overall performance of SMEs.

This study delineated three essential pivotal managerial implications for SME founders, managers, and the broader Saudi SME sector. At first, decision-makers in small- to medium-sized enterprises, whether involved in strategic, tactical, or operational capacities, must deepen their understanding of diverse KPIs and their effective application. Second, SMEs must recognize the importance of web analytics tools in improving performance measurements. Lastly, considering the substantial economic contribution of SMEs in Saudi Arabia, the findings of this study aim to fortify the sector by advocating for the adoption of web analytics tools, underscored by the seven key motivators.

The generalizability of the findings among SMEs in Saudi Arabia is limited. This limitation requires future researchers to expand the sample size and encompass a wider range of industries and countries. It is important to note that this study specifically focused on the e-commerce sector in Saudi Arabia.

REFERENCES

- [1] "Over 750,000 SMEs operating in Saudi Arabia, a 15% increase on 2021," Small & Medium Enterprises General Authority, Monsha'at report, Jun. 2022. [Online]. Available: <http://monshaat.gov.sa/en/node/9515>.
- [2] L. A. Hussein, A. S. Baharudin, S. Kiumarsi, and M. F. Hilmi, "Factors Influencing the Intention to Continue using B2B e-Commerce in Manufacturing SMEs," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 5528–5533, Apr. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3373>.
- [3] S. Kaabi and R. Jallouli, "Overview of E-commerce Technologies, Data Analysis Capabilities and Marketing Knowledge," in *Digital Economy. Emerging Technologies and Business Innovation*, Beirut, Lebanon, 2019, pp. 183–193, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-30874-2_14.
- [4] M. Bianchini and V. Michalkova, "Data Analytics in SMEs: Trends and Policies," OECD, Paris, France, Jun. 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1787/1de6c6a7-en>.
- [5] S. Coleman, R. Göb, G. Manco, A. Pievatolo, X. Tort-Martorell, and M. S. Reis, "How Can SMEs Benefit from Big Data? Challenges and a Path Forward," *Quality and Reliability Engineering International*, vol. 32, no. 6, pp. 2151–2164, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1002/qre.2008>.
- [6] S. Y. Coleman, "Data-Mining Opportunities for Small and Medium Enterprises with Official Statistics in the UK," *Journal of Official Statistics*, vol. 32, no. 4, pp. 849–865, Dec. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1515/jos-2016-0044>.
- [7] M. Dittert, R. C. Härtling, C. Reichstein, and C. Bayer, "A Data Analytics Framework for Business in Small and Medium-Sized Organizations," in *Intelligent Decision Technologies 2017*, Vilamoura, Portugal, 2018, pp. 169–181, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-59424-8_16.
- [8] M. Nasrollahi, J. Ramezani, and M. Sadraei, "The Impact of Big Data Adoption on SMEs' Performance," *Big Data and Cognitive Computing*, vol. 5, no. 4, Dec. 2021, Art. no. 68, <https://doi.org/10.3390/bdcc5040068>.
- [9] W. Boufenneche, M. Hebboul, and O. Benabderrahmane, "Web Analytics Tools for e-Commerce: An Overview and Comparative Analysis," in *International Conference on Managing Business Through Web Analytics*, 2022, pp. 51–72, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-06971-0_5.
- [10] U. P. Jyothi, S. Bonthu, and B. V. Prasanthi, "A Study on Raise of Web Analytics and its Benefits," *International Journal of Computer Sciences and Engineering*, vol. 5, no. 10, pp. 59–64, Oct. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.26438/ijcse/v5i10.5964>.
- [11] C. Truong, H. Phuong, N. Thi, and H. Trang, "Web analytics tools and benefits for entrepreneurs," BSc Thesis, Lahti University of Applied Sciences, Lahti, Finland, 2017.
- [12] "7 Must Have Ecommerce Analytics Tools," *Ecommerce Platforms*, Jan. 08, 2015. <https://ecommerce-platforms.com/ecommerce-selling-advice/7-must-ecommerce-analytics-tools>.
- [13] J. Maintz and F. Zaumseil, "Using Web analytics for content marketing performance measurement," presented at the 5th International Conference on Contemporary Marketing Issues, Thessaloniki, Greece, 2017.
- [14] J. Järvinen and H. Karjaluoto, "The use of Web analytics for digital marketing performance measurement," *Industrial Marketing Management*, vol. 50, pp. 117–127, Oct. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2015.04.009>.
- [15] B. Plaza, "Google Analytics for measuring website performance," *Tourism Management*, vol. 32, no. 3, pp. 477–481, Jun. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2010.03.015>.
- [16] Z. Hosseini, S. Mohammadi, and H. Safari, "An Assessment of the Impact of Information Technology on Marketing and Advertising," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 2526–2531, Feb. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1620>.
- [17] N. S. Redkina, "The development tendencies of web analytics tools," *Automatic Documentation and Mathematical Linguistics*, vol. 51, no. 3, pp. 112–116, Jun. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.3103/S0005105517030050>.
- [18] G. Zheng and S. Peltsverger, "Web Analytics Overview," in *Encyclopedia of Information Science and Technology, Third Edition*, Hersley, PA, USA: IGI Global, 2015.
- [19] J. Burby, A. Brown, and WAA Standards Committee, "Web Analytics Definitions," Web Analytics Association, Washington, DC, USA, Aug. 2017.
- [20] R. Sharda, D. Delen, and E. Turban, *Business intelligence, analytics, and data science: a managerial perspective*, Fourth edition. New York, NY: Pearson, 2018.
- [21] H. Singal, S. Kohli, and A. K. Sharma, "Web analytics: State-of-art & literature assessment," in *2014 5th International Conference - Confluence The Next Generation Information Technology Summit (Confluence)*, Noida, India, Sep. 2014, pp. 24–29, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CONFLUENCE.2014.6949041>.
- [22] I. Bekavac and D. Garbin Praničević, "Web analytics tools and web metrics tools: An overview and comparative analysis," *Croatian Operational Research Review*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 373–386, Oct. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.17535/crorr.2015.0029>.
- [23] A. Kaushik, *Web Analytics: An Hour a Day*. Indianapolis, IN, USA: John Wiley & Sons, 2007.
- [24] L. Kumar, H. Singh, and R. Kaur, "Web analytics and metrics: a survey," in *Proceedings of the International Conference on Advances in*

- Computing, Communications and Informatics, Chennai, India, May 2012, pp. 966–971, <https://doi.org/10.1145/2345396.2345552>.
- [25] "Website Traffic - Check and Analyze Any Website," *Similarweb*. <https://www.similarweb.com/>.
- [26] K. Nakatani and T. Chuang, "A web analytics tool selection method: an analytical hierarchy process approach," *Internet Research*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 171–186, Jan. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1108/10662241111123757>.
- [27] "W3Techs - extensive and reliable web technology surveys." <https://w3techs.com/>.
- [28] M. M. Savitha and S. M. Illuru, "Google Analytics," *International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering Technology and Science*, vol. 4, no. 6, pp. 4319–4323, Jun. 2022.
- [29] D. Heller, "Web analytics: functions, KPIs and reports in SMEs," BSc Thesis, Universität Koblenz, Koblenz, Germany, 2016.
- [30] "Page-Analytics Chrome extension - Analytics Help." <https://support.google.com/analytics/answer/6047802?hl=en#zippy=%2Cin-this-article>.
- [31] "Hotjar: Website Heatmaps & Behavior Analytics Tools." <https://www.hotjar.com/>.
- [32] M. del M. R. García, J. García-Nieto, and J. F. Aldana-Montes, "An ontology-based data integration approach for web analytics in e-commerce," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 63, pp. 20–34, Nov. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2016.06.034>.
- [33] A. Ferrini and J. J. Mohr, "Uses, Limitations, and Trends in Web Analytics," in *Handbook of Research on Web Log Analysis*, Hersley, PA, USA: IGI Global, 2009, pp. 124–142.
- [34] M. Nastasia and C. Mironeasa, "Key Performance Indicators in Small and Medium Sized Enterprises," *TEHNOMUS - New Technologies and Products in Machine Manufacturing Technologies*, pp. 46–53, 2016.
- [35] V. Kumar and G. A. Ogunmola, "Web Analytics for Knowledge Creation: A Systematic Review of Tools, Techniques, and Practices," *International Journal of Cyber Behavior, Psychology and Learning (IJCIBPL)*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 1–14, Jan. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.4018/IJCIBPL.2020010101>.
- [36] "Conversion rate: Definition - Google Ads Help." https://support.google.com/google-ads/answer/2684489?hl=en&ref_topic=24937.
- [37] D. Chaffey, D. Edmundson-Bird, and T. Hemphill, *Digital Business and E-commerce Management*. London, UK: Pearson UK, 2019.
- [38] "Zid App Market," *Zid App Market*. <https://apps.zid.sa>.
- [39] M. F. Mubarak, F. A. Shaikh, M. Mubarik, K. A. Samo, and S. Mastoi, "The Impact of Digital Transformation on Business Performance: A Study of Pakistani SMEs," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 5056–5061, Dec. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3201>.
- [40] S. B. Merriam and R. S. Grenier, "Introduction to Qualitative Research," in *Qualitative Research in Practice: Examples for Discussion and Analysis*, Hoboken, NJ, USA: John Wiley & Sons, 2019, pp. 3–18.
- [41] "Kingdom of Saudi Arabia - Ministry of Commerce," Ministry of Commerce, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, Dec. 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://mc.gov.sa:443/en/mediacenter/News/Pages/13-12-16-03.aspx>.
- [42] B. Marshall, P. Cardon, A. Poddar, and R. Fontenot, "Does Sample Size Matter in Qualitative Research?: A Review of Qualitative Interviews in is Research," *Journal of Computer Information Systems*, vol. 54, no. 1, pp. 11–22, Sep. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1080/08874417.2013.11645667>.
- [43] V. Braun and V. Clarke, "Thematic analysis," in *APA handbook of research methods in psychology: Research designs: Quantitative, qualitative, neuropsychological, and biological*, 2nd ed., vol. 2, Washington, DC, USA: American Psychological Association, 2023, pp. 65–81.

A Low Noise Amplifier with 27 dB Gain and 1.78 dB Noise for Satellite Communications with 0.1 μm GaAs pHEMT Technology

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ABSTRACT

This paper proposes a design of a 38 GHz Low Noise Amplifier (LNA) that uses a three-stage common source inductive degeneration topology with a gain of 27 dB and noise figure of 1.78 dB using 0.1 μm GaAs pHEMT as an active device. The novelty of the design is the usage of inductive load in series with the resistor instead of resistive load, resulting in higher gain performance. A recent pp1010 active device of WIN foundry was explored for this LNA design at the Q band. The high transition frequency offered by this technology succeeded in obtaining competitive results with a minimum number of cells. The designed LNA obtained the lowest noise compared to other recently published LNA designs at the Q band. The total power consumption of this design is 57 mW.

Keywords-*pseudomorphic high electron mobility transistor (pHEMT); gallium arsenide (GaAs); low noise amplifier; inductive source degeneration; common source topology; radio frequency (RF)*

I. INTRODUCTION

The huge demand of Q, V bands for satellite communications stimulated the design of millimeter wave applications. The low noise amplifier is a critical and essential component of millimeter wave applications of satellite communications [1-3]. BICMOS and MESFET technologies were able to support the MMIC LNA design only up to RF micro meter level (3 to 30 GHz) [4], but the MMIC LNA design at the milli meter level (30 GHz – 300 GHz) is supported only by HEMT technologies [5]. GaAs, GaN, and InP technologies are the mostly used HEMT technologies for RF design. GaAs and InP technologies [6, 7] are preferred for LNA design, whereas GaN technology is ideal for power amplifier designs [8]. However, GaAs technology is significant for LNA design in obtaining low noise figure with low productive cost and less fragile nature.

EM waves travel through longer distances before reaching the base station. These signals get degraded and attenuated during their travel. Hence satellite communication demands a high sensitive receiver at the base station to detect very weak signals received from satellites. As LNA is the first block of satellite communication receiver, the entire system

performance depends on the gain and noise of LNA. From the past research it is observed that most of the LNA designs are of CS configuration [9, 10]. Very few designs were identified with other topologies like common gate [11], self-bias [12], current reuse [13] and cascoded [14] topologies. From the past works, it is noticed that other than CS topologies obtained less gain. This is the motivation behind the selection of CS topology for the proposed design. However, the three-stage common source topology LNA [15] with resistive load resulted in low gain. Hence, the proposed LNA used common source topology with inductive load in series with the resistor to obtain more gain. Three-stage LNA with common source topology using 0.15 μm GaAs HEMT technology [16] obtained gain of 23 dB and 3.8 dB noise figure. Using 0.1 μm GaAs HEMT technology obtained better performance than [16]. Features like highest transition frequency and maximum oscillation frequency of HEMT from the WIN foundry also enhanced the performance of the proposed work.

II. TECHNOLOGY

Pp1010 is the selected HEMT for the LNA design. In order to obtain low noise and high gain, the device has to be biased at 10 percent of IDSS. The selected pp1010 is biased with V_{gs} of

-0.4 V and V_{ds} of 1V, obtained gain of 9.546 dB and 1.3 dB noise figure. This pHEMT can be operated up to maximum drain bias of -4V with gate to drain breakdown voltage of 9.6V. The pp1010 used in the design of LNA has a gate length of 0.1 μm and was generated using the E beam process with substrate thickness of 50 μm. Channel is made up of InGaAs for this particular HEMT with maximum drain bias of 4V. HEMT is fully passivated using nitride as a dielectric for fully passivated Metal Insulator Metal (MIM) capacitors. The inter connections have high density and two thick metal air bridges. At maximum transconductance of 750 mS/mm, the maximum drain current is 760 mA/mm with V_{gs} of -0.5 V.

III. CIRCUIT DESIGN

The most important key factors in designing an LNA at Q band are: 1) The HEMT performance and 2) the circuit design to obtain low noise, high gain, and good stability. The first factor is attained by selecting 0.1 μm GaAs pHEMT and the second factor is attained by using source inductive degeneration in all three stages with common source configuration. However, the usage of high value inductors at the source for high stability degrades the gain value. Hence, there is a trade-off between stability and gain.

Fig. 1. 38 GHz three stage Q band LNA.

The LNA design starts from selecting the transistor with maximum transition frequency and low noise figure. pp1010 satisfies these features in 0.1 μm GaAs pHEMT technology. The proper gate width and number of fingers give a tradeoff between maximum gain, minimum noise, and Rollet stability factor. For the selected device size of 2x50 μm and bias values of V_{gs} = -0.4 V and V_{ds}=1V, the pp1010 HEMT offers maximum gain of 9.54 dB and, low noise of 1.3 dB. The schematic block diagram of a 38 GHz three stage Q band LNA is shown in Figure 1. The three-stage Q band LNA was designed by cascading the three single stages. All the three individual single stages are applied with the same value of inductive source degeneration. Each individual single stage obtained a gain of 9.2 dB and 1.56 dB noise figure. Concentrating on maximum gain of the system requirement, we opted the three-stage cascaded common source configuration. Focusing on low noise figure, we selected all the three stages with device periphery of 2x50 μm. With these alignments, finally the cascaded three stages obtained a gain of 27.45 dB and 1.78 dB noise.

IV. DESIGN ANALYSIS

Stability check of LNA at millimeter wave frequencies is compulsory because of mismatch conditions. The Rollet factor (*k*) is the measure of stability of a two port network. The necessary and sufficient conditions for stability are:

$$k > 1$$

$$1 - |s_{11}|^2 > |s_{12}s_{21}| \tag{1}$$

$$1 - |s_{22}|^2 > |s_{12}s_{21}| \tag{2}$$

where:

$$k = \frac{1 - |s_{11}|^2 - |s_{22}|^2 + |\Delta|^2}{2|s_{12}s_{21}|}$$

$$\Delta = s_{11}s_{22} - s_{12}s_{21}$$

where *s*₁₁, *s*₂₂, *s*₁₂, and *s*₂₁ are the *s* parameters of the LNA.

Fig. 2. Stability curve of the pp1010 HEMT.

From the stability curve it is observed that the pp1010 HEMT is unstable from 0 to 33.4 GHz. The stability at low frequency can be analyzed from the frequency stability model.

Fig. 3. Low frequency stability.

Fig. 4. Small signal equivalent.

From the small signal equivalent circuit, the assumed output is fully decoupled and the input impedance is given by:

$$Z_{in} = \frac{Z_L + \frac{1}{j\omega C_f}}{1 + g_m Z_L} \quad (3)$$

For $Z_L = j\omega L$ and if $\frac{1}{j\omega C_f} > j\omega L$ then:

$$Z_{in} = \frac{1}{(1 + g_m \omega L)^2} \left(\frac{1}{j\omega C_f} - \frac{g_m L}{C_f} \right) \quad (4)$$

Similarly, the assumed input is fully decoupled and the output impedance is given by:

$$Z_{out} = \frac{Z_L + \frac{1}{j\omega L}}{1 + g_m Z_L} \quad (5)$$

For $Z_L = R + j\omega L$:

$$Z_{out} = \frac{R(1 + g_m R) - \frac{g_m L}{C_f}}{(1 + g_m R)^2 + g_m \omega^2 L^2} \quad (6)$$

By assuming $g_m R > 1$ and $R^2 > \frac{L}{C}$, the Z_{out} will be positive.

From the analysis section, the following changes are performed in the proposed design.

A. The Proposed Design

Selecting large series bias inductance values will reduce the negative resistance component at all frequencies. This is a viable case for the input side, as shown in Figure 5. But selecting large bias inductor at the output side does not work out, since the modulated current flows through the output side. The proposed design used an inductor connected in series with the shunt resistor to avoid gain degradation of in-band frequency range, as shown in Figure 6. For a given source impedance, it is trivial to read out the noise figure and the available gain of a two port network. The trade-off between them becomes intuitive in a Smith chart. An appropriate tradeoff is obtained while selecting the source impedance of $26.302 + j27.822 \Omega$.

Fig. 5. Schematic diagram after adding R, L at the input side.

Figure 7 shows the schematic of common source inductive degenerate LNA with matching networks at the input and

output side. Matching networks are designed with matching stubs at gate and drain side. The obtained source impedance is $26 + j27 \Omega$. A stub matching network is introduced at the input side to transform 50Ω to the required impedance. Similarly at the output side, a matching network is introduced, which would transform the output Z_{out} to 50Ω . Source degeneration is obtained by connecting an inductor at the source side. Spiral inductors are used at input and output side for biasing. Low frequency stability obtained by connecting a resistance in series with the spiral inductor at the gate side. The proposed design avoided gain degradation in band frequency by connecting a shunt resistor at the drain side in series with the spiral inductors as shown in Figure 7.

Fig. 6. Schematic diagram after adding a shunt resistor at the output side.

Fig. 7. Schematic diagram after adding matching circuits.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The EM simulated gain (S_{21}) behavior of the designed three-stage LNA is shown in Figure 8. The final three stage Q-band LNA achieved a gain of 27.031 dB at 38 GHz and has better performance even when compared to the state of the art performance while meeting the design specifications. The simulated results of the Input Return Loss (IRL) and the Output Return Loss (ORL) of the MMIC Q band three-stage LNA are shown in Figure 10. IRL (S_{11}) of -7.937 dB and a very high ORL (S_{22}) of -31.609 dB are obtained at 38 GHz. With the state-of-the-art performance, this proposed work achieved a very high value of ORL. The simulated noise figure of MMIC

Q band final three stage LNA is shown in Figure 9. A NF of 1.561 dB is obtained at 38 GHz frequency. The obtained noise figure result is very competitive compared to the state-of-the-art (Table I). To the best of our knowledge, most reported works have noise figures around 2 dB. The presented work obtained noise less than 2 dB.

Fig. 8. Gain of 38GHz Q band LNA.

Fig. 9. Noise figure of 38GHz Q band LNA.

Fig. 10. Input output return losses of 38 GHz Q band LNA.

The final layout of the three-stage LNA is provided in Figure 11. The layout of the MMIC Q band three-stage LNA

results in a chip size of 2.5×2.7 mm². The chip size is comparable with the state of the art.

Fig. 11. Layout of the three stage Q band LNA.

Various design solutions of LNA around the Q band are compared with the proposed LNA and the results are shown in Table I. The concerned parameters with the state of the art performance are gain and noise. Compared to the previously reported LNAs, the proposed LNA gives good matching, low output return loss, high gain, and low overall noise figure. Authors in [12, 17] have used a different mHEMT technology but the acquired gain is less compared to the one of the proposed work. The design in [18] using mHEMT obtained a gain almost equal to the proposed work's, but it was designed with four stages of common source configuration, whereas the proposed work obtained the same gain value using three stages. Authors in [16] used the GaAs substrate and acquired comparable gain dimensions but IRL and ORL were not given. Authors in [15] obtained good IRL and ORL but with less gain. Among the cited papers from Table I, the proposed work exhibited better performance in terms of output return loss, noise figure, and gain.

VI. DISCUSSION

The novelty of the design is the usage of inductive load in series with the resistor instead of resistor load. The shunt resistor avoids large voltage drops through load and helps in obtaining a high gain of 27.45 dB. The designed features of the proposed LNA are suitable for satellite communication.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

In summary, a suitable MMIC LNA was realized for a multi gigabit satellite communication receiver. The design strategy used inductive load in series with the resistor for improving the band frequency gain. The designed LNA performance has been compared with the state-of-the-art results. The proposed LNA exhibits a gain of 27.475dB and 1.78 dB noise figure at 38 GHz with a low ORL of -31.609 dB. Noise and output return loss were improved by 10% and 16%, respectively in comparison to the standard design values of 2dB and -12 dB.

TABLE I. COMPARISON SUMMARY

Ref	Technology	Freq (GHz)	Gain (dB)	IRL (dB)	ORL (dB)	Power (mW)	Noise (dB)	Chip area (mm ²)
[16]	0.15µm GaAs pHEMT	28-50	23	-	-	62	3.8	2×1.5
[12]	0.07 µm AlGaAs/ InGaAs mHEMT	42-46	19	-25	-27	40	1.5	3×1.2
[15]	0.1µm GaAs pHEMT	40-51	16.5	-11	-11	80	2	3×1
[17]	0.07µm GaAs mHEMT	47-52	17	-20	-15	-	2	-
[18]	0.05µm GaAs mHEMT	30-50	27.5	-10	-12	240	2	2×1
Proposed	0.1µm GaAs pHEMT	36-40	27.4	-7.937	-31.60	80	1.78	2.5×2.7

From this work, it is evident that 0.1 µm GaAs pHEMT technology can be successfully extended to produce LNA at millimeter wave frequency range for a satellite communication receiver with better performance, provided that appropriate design approach and proper device models are developed.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Narimani and L. Farhoudi, "Design of a Self-Phased Quadrifilar Helix Antenna for Satellite Communication," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 2273–2276, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1569>.
- [2] A. Bousselmi, A. Gharsallah, and T. P. Vuong, "A Novel High-Gain Quad-Band Antenna with AMC Metasurface for Satellite Positioning Systems," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 4581–4585, Oct. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2933>.
- [3] A. Alogla, M. A. H. Eleiwa, and H. Alshortan, "Design and Evaluation of Transmitting Antennas for Solar Power Satellite Systems," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 7950–7956, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4607>.
- [4] B. K. Ko and K. Lee, "A comparative study on the various monolithic low noise amplifier circuit topologies for RF and microwave applications," *IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 31, no. 8, pp. 1220–1225, Dec. 1996, <https://doi.org/10.1109/4.508274>.
- [5] J. V. Terán Collantes, L. de la Fuente, B. Aja, and E. Artal, "Cryogenic broadband Q-band MMIC low-noise amplifier," in *2016 11th European Microwave Integrated Circuits Conference (EuMIC)*, London, UK, Jul. 2016, pp. 77–80, <https://doi.org/10.1109/EuMIC.2016.7777494>.
- [6] Y.-T. Chou, C.-C. Chiong, and H. Wang, "A Q-band LNA with 55.7% bandwidth for radio astronomy applications in 0.15-µm GaAs pHEMT process," in *2016 IEEE International Symposium on Radio-Frequency Integration Technology (RFIT)*, Taipei, Taiwan, Dec. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1109/RFIT.2016.7578197>.
- [7] P. M. Smith *et al.*, "Advances in InP HEMT technology for high frequency applications," in *Conference Proceedings. 2001 International Conference on Indium Phosphide and Related Materials. 13th IPRM (Cat. No.01CH37198)*, Nara, Japan, Feb. 2001, pp. 9–14, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIPRM.2001.929005>.
- [8] K. Husna Hamza and D. Nirmal, "A review of GaN HEMT broadband power amplifiers," *AEU - International Journal of Electronics and Communications*, vol. 116, Mar. 2020, Art. no. 153040, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aeue.2019.153040>.
- [9] R. Limacher *et al.*, "Broadband low-noise amplifiers for K- and Q-bands using 0.2 µm InP HEMT MMIC technology," in *IEEE Compound Semiconductor Integrated Circuit Symposium, 2004.*, Monterey, CA, USA, Jul. 2004, pp. 305–308, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CSICS.2004.1392575>.
- [10] H. Uchida *et al.*, "Ka-band multistage MMIC low-noise amplifier using source inductors with different values for each stage," *IEEE Microwave and Guided Wave Letters*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 71–72, Oct. 1999, <https://doi.org/10.1109/75.755050>.
- [11] M. Sato *et al.*, "Q-Band InAlGa/GaN LNA using current reuse topology," in *2016 IEEE MTT-S International Microwave Symposium (IMS)*, San Francisco, CA, USA, Feb. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MWSYM.2016.7540307>.
- [12] M. Vittori, G. Polli, W. Ciccognani, S. Colangeli, A. Salvucci, and E. Limiti, "Q-band self-biased MMIC LNAs using a 70 nm InGaAs/AlGaAs process," in *2017 IEEE Asia Pacific Microwave Conference (APMC)*, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, Aug. 2017, pp. 630–633, <https://doi.org/10.1109/APMC.2017.8251525>.
- [13] M. Sato, T. Takahashi, and T. Hirose, "68–110-GHz-Band Low-Noise Amplifier Using Current Reuse Topology," *IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques*, vol. 58, no. 7, pp. 1910–1916, Jul. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TMTT.2010.2050374>.
- [14] C.-C. Chang and Y.-C. Chiang, "Low-noise amplifier with 12.1 dB gain and 5.456 dB NF for V-band applications in GaAs 0.15µm pHEMT process," in *2012 IEEE International Symposium on Radio-Frequency Integration Technology (RFIT)*, Singapore, Aug. 2012, pp. 16–18, <https://doi.org/10.1109/RFIT.2012.6401599>.
- [15] L. Pantoli, A. Barigelli, G. Leuzzi, and F. Vitulli, "Analysis and design of a Q/V-band low-noise amplifier in GaAs-based 0.1 µm pHEMT technology," *IET Microwaves, Antennas & Propagation*, vol. 10, no. 14, pp. 1500–1506, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1049/iet-map.2016.0422>.
- [16] Y.-T. Chou, C.-C. Chiong, and H. Wang, "A Q-band LNA with 55.7% bandwidth for radio astronomy applications in 0.15-µm GaAs pHEMT process," in *2016 IEEE International Symposium on Radio-Frequency Integration Technology (RFIT)*, Taipei, Taiwan, Dec. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1109/RFIT.2016.7578197>.
- [17] W. Ciccognani, P. E. Longhi, S. Colangeli, E. Limiti, and S. M. Ieee, "Q/V band LNA for satellite on-board space applications using a 70 nanometers GaAs mHEMT commercial technology," *Microwave and Optical Technology Letters*, vol. 60, no. 9, pp. 2185–2190, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1002/mop.31317>.
- [18] D. Schwantuschke *et al.*, "Q- and E-band amplifier MMICs for satellite communication," in *2014 IEEE MTT-S International Microwave Symposium (IMS2014)*, Tampa, FL, USA, Jun. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MWSYM.2014.6848322>.

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Improving the Impact Resistance through Annealing in PLA 3D Printed Parts

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ABSTRACT

This study conducts an experimental exploration and thorough analysis of the influence of annealing on the impact resistance of PLA 3D-printed components. The investigation extends its scope to encompass the influence of printing parameters, specifically layer thickness and infill percentage. The research highlights that the impact resistance of annealed 3D printed PLA components is predominantly influenced by the infill percentage, with the highest impact energy observed at a full 100% infill. It is noticeable that the application of annealing post-processing heat treatment results in a remarkable, up to threefold, increase of the impact energy highlighting its potential efficacy as a viable technique for enhancing the mechanical integrity of PLA 3D printed products. Consequently, this study establishes annealing as a promising methodology, particularly for PLA 3D printing applications that encounter significant mechanical loads.

Keywords-3D printing; FDM; annealing; Charpy test; PLA

I. INTRODUCTION

The impact resistance of polylactic acid (PLA) is a critical parameter that significantly influences its practical applications. PLA, while widely appreciated for its biodegradability and compatibility with additive manufacturing techniques like 3D printing, does exhibit a notable limitation in impact strength [1], making PLA-based products susceptible to fracture or failure under certain mechanical loadings. Therefore, improvements in this direction are of significant industrial and technological importance [2]. In the context of its various applications, PLA's impact resistance plays a crucial role in determining its suitability for specific uses. For instance, in applications where structural integrity and robustness are dominant, such as in engineering components or load-bearing parts, PLA's inherent brittleness might impose constraints on its effective application. The low impact strength could lead to premature failure or reduced durability in applications involving dynamic loading or impact events [3-9]. Efforts to enhance PLA's impact resistance are of considerable interest from both industrial and technological perspectives. Various strategies, including material modifications, blending with impact modifiers, and processing optimization, are explored to address this limitation.

Annealing, serving as a heat treatment technique, stands out as a primary method of PLA modification, due to its cost-effectiveness [2, 11-13]. Annealing involves subjecting the polymer to a specific temperature range between the glass transition and the melting point, and maintaining this temperature for a specified duration. Other factors, such as printing parameters, can have a great influence on the mechanical behavior of 3D printed parts [13-22]. Charpy tests were performed in [1], on 3D-printed samples made of PLA and ABS, investigating the influence of layer thickness and infill percentage on their impact resistance. In [23], an impact test was executed to quantify the absorbed energy in the plastic deformation within 3D printed PLA components, encompassing diverse combinations of infill patterns and densities. The findings derived from the experimental assessment using the Izod impact test indicated that the highest energy absorption is achieved when the infill density reaches 85% across all infill patterns. The experimental investigation in [24] provides insights into the impact performance of PLA and PETG specimens manufactured through additive processes, revealing that PLA specimens generally experienced higher impact forces during testing. Authors in [25] focused on the influence of varying layer thicknesses (0.10, 0.20, 0.30, 0.40, 0.50 mm) and different print orientations (upright, flatwise,

edgewise) on the impact strength of ABS, PLA, PET-G, and PC produced through additive manufacturing. Remarkably, the modification of layer thickness was found to exert the most pronounced effect on PC, followed sequentially by PET-G, ABS, and PLA. Polycarbonate PC demonstrated the highest impact strength, particularly when employing a layer thickness of 0.30 mm. On the other hand, PLA exhibited the least resistance to impact forces. It was also found that the upright print orientation yielded the lowest impact strength results among the evaluated orientations. The experimental results of [12] highlight the significant influence of carbon fiber reinforcement and infill density on the impact strength of annealed PETG and CFPETG. At 100% infill density, the annealing process increased the impact strength by 5.5% (for PETG samples) and 12% (for CFPETG samples). Following the heat treatment process at 80 °C and 90 °C, a substantial enhancement in impact strength was achieved in [2], with increases of 97.80% and 133.20% compared with as-built PLA specimens. Authors in [26] assessed how the impact performance of 3D printed nylon composites reinforced with continuous carbon, glass, and Kevlar fibers, produced using the FDM technique, is influenced by build orientation, layer thickness, and fiber volume content.

From the literature review presented above, it can be observed that a limited number of studies focused on the impact behavior of 3D printed parts, even less regarding the influence of post processing heat treatment. The aim of this paper is to analyze, in an innovative manner, the influence of annealing heat treatment correlated with printing parameters, such as layer thickness on impact resistance of PLA 3D printed parts. By meticulously investigating how annealing interacts with the printing parameters, the study sheds light on a previously unexplored dimension of optimizing impact resistance in PLA 3D printed parts.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The technical specifications (Table I) were provided from the Raise filament producer through data sheets. A Raise E2 3D printer was used with a volume capacity of 330 × 240 × 240 mm. The printing parameters are presented in Table II. The samples dimensional characteristics can be seen in Figure 1(a). A notch type A was included in the design of the sample with radius $r_N = (0.25 \pm 0.05)$ mm.

TABLE I. 3D PRINTED SAMPLE CHARACTERISTICS

Parameters	Material specifications
Nozzle diameter	0.40 mm
Build orientation	Flat
Top solid layers	4 layers
Bottom solid layers	4 layers
Outline/perimeters shell	3 outlines
Internal fill pattern	Lines
External fill pattern	Rectilinear
Internal infill angle offsets	45°-135°
Extruder temperature	210 °C
Heated bed temperature	60 °C
Default printing speed	70 mm/s
Cooling fans	On
Filament diameter	1.75 mm
Filament density	1.24 g/cm ³

TABLE II. 3D PRINTING PARAMETERS

Constant parameters	Variable parameters
Build orientation X-Y	Layer thickness, $L_t = 0.10$ mm/0.15 mm/0.20 mm
Print speed – 80 mm/s	Infill percentage, $I_p = 50\%/75\%/100\%$
Deposition temperature – 210 °C	
Infill model- lines, 45° orientated	

Fig. 1. The samples used for experiments: (a) dimensions, (b) actual samples subjected to annealing.

The annealing procedure involved subjecting the samples to a temperature of 75 °C (slightly above the glass transition temperature of PLA) for 3 hr, followed by a gradual and controlled cooling process (Figure 1(b)). The samples were uniformly cooled together in the oven of Figure 2. The impact testing was done at the Liea laboratory, within ISIM Timișoara, on an Instron Pendulum Charpy tester (Figure 3), according to ISO 179-1:2010(E) [27].

Fig. 2. The oven used for the heat treatment.

Fig. 3. Impact testing machine.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We aimed to examine how printing parameters and annealing heat treatment affect the impact resistance of PLA 3D printed parts, assessing the combined influence of these variables. For every specific group of process parameters, a set of five specimens was prepared. The outcome of the mechanical test was determined based on the average impact strength values derived from these specimens. The values of maximal energy absorbed for each combination of printing parameters, both for annealed and as-built PLA evaluated samples can be seen in Table III. The total absorbed energy of the impact is calculated by [26]:

$$E_T = mg(h_0 - h_f) \pm 0.2 \text{ (J)} \tag{1}$$

where E_T is the total absorbed energy, m is the mass, g is the gravitational acceleration, h_0 is the original height, and h_f is the final height.

TABLE III. AVERAGE VALUES OF PLA IMPACT ENERGY

Lt [mm]	Ip [%]	Energy [J]		Difference %
		Annealed samples	As-built samples	
0.10	50	0.162	0.072	125.07
	75	0.228	0.088	157.62
	100	0.220	0.078	181.29
0.15	50	0.167	0.078	114.10
	75	0.235	0.075	213.63
	100	0.311	0.081	283.72
0.20	50	0.190	0.076	148.97
	75	0.202	0.080	152.84
	100	0.278	0.082	238.82

Figure 4 depicts the average impact energy values in relation to the printing parameters (layer thickness and infill percentage) both for as-built specimens and for annealed specimens, providing a clear understanding of the influence of the different factors.

Fig. 4. Comparative values of impact energy obtained for as-built and annealed PLA samples.

The difference percentage between the impact energy of annealed and as-built samples for each combination of printing parameters is shown in Figure 5, in order to better visualize the influence of heat-treatment on the impact behavior of 3D printed parts. It can be observed that the impact energy increases by 125.10% and 283.70% (corresponding to the best

optimal combination of printing parameters, namely 0.15 mm layer thickness and 100% infill percentage). A similar significant increase (from 97.80% to 133.20%) of PLA impact strength was obtained in [2].

For each layer thickness, the smallest increase of impact strength for the annealed specimens compared with the as-built ones was obtained at 50% infill percentage, while the greater influence of annealing treatment was observed at 100% infill percentage. This finding implies that annealing can be a highly effective method for increasing the impact resistance of PLA 3D printed parts.

Fig. 5. The percentage variation of impact energy after annealing treatment.

Fig. 6. The influence of printing parameters on impact energy for as-built samples.

Fig. 7. The influence of printing parameters on impact energy for annealed samples.

For the as-built samples, the maximum impact energy value was obtained at 75% infill percentage and 0.1 mm layer thickness, while the minimum value corresponds to 50% infill percentage and 0.10 mm layer thickness (Figure 6). For the annealed samples, the maximum impact energy value was obtained at 100% infill percentage and 0.15 mm layer thickness, while the minimum value corresponds to 50% infill percentage and 0.10 mm layer thickness (Figure 7). It can be also observed that the impact energy of annealed PLA 3D printed parts increases with infill percentage and for each infill percentage the maximum value of impact energy is obtained for a layer thickness of 0.15 mm.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study innovatively investigates experimentally the previously unexplored relationship between annealing heat treatment, printing parameters (particularly layer thickness and infill percentage), and impact resistance in PLA 3D printed parts, addressing a significant research gap and providing valuable insights for optimizing mechanical performance.

It is noteworthy to emphasize that the impact energy of PLA printed components can be highly influenced by multiple variables, encompassing printing parameters (which were investigated in this study through changes in layer height and infill percentage) [26], and post-processing heat treatments.

The main factor influencing the impact resistance of annealed 3D printed parts is the infill percentage, the maximum impact energy corresponding to 100% infill percentage.

Since the impact energy increased up to three times due to the annealing treatment, it can be concluded that annealing is a suitable methodology to be applied for PLA 3D printing products used in applications that involve high mechanical loads.

The findings highlight the practicality and versatility of annealing as a cost-effective and efficient method for enhancing the mechanical integrity of PLA 3D printed products, which can have widespread applications in various industries [2].

Further studies will be performed to explore the effect of different annealing temperatures and durations on the impact resistance to determine the most effective annealing parameters. Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) analysis will be applied in order to assess 3D printed PLA and heat treatments stems from their capacity to offer complementary data. TGA primarily concentrates on tracking the material's weight loss and how it decomposes under heating conditions, while DSC sheds light on shifts in the material's heat capacity and transitions between phases. When investigating the impact of heat treatments on 3D printed PLA, employing both techniques in unison will grant a holistic comprehension of how the material reacts to elevated temperatures. For instance, TGA will reveal the temperature at which substantial decomposition takes place, while DSC can accentuate alterations in the material's thermal transitions. These combined analyses will prove instrumental in refining heat treatments processes for specific purposes or gauging the material's adaptability to particular thermal settings.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. G. Zisopol, N. Ion, and A. I. Portoaca, "Comparison of the Charpy Resilience of Two 3D Printed Materials: A Study on the Impact Resistance of Plastic Parts," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 10781–10784, Jun. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5876>.
- [2] C. B. B. Luna, D. D. Siqueira, E. M. Araújo, and R. M. R. Wellen, "Annealing efficacy on PLA. Insights on mechanical, thermomechanical and crystallinity characters," *MOMENTO*, no. 62, pp. 1–17, Jan. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.15446/mo.n62.89099>.
- [3] D. G. Zisopol, A. Dumitrescu, and C.N. Trifan, *Ecotehnologie. Noțiuni teoretice, aplicații și studii de caz*. Ploiesti, Romania: Editura Universității Petrol - Gaze din Ploiești, 2010.
- [4] D.G. Zisopol and A. Dumitrescu, *Ecotehnologie: Studii de caz*. Ploiesti, Romania: Editura Universității Petrol-Gaze din Ploiești, 2020.
- [5] D. G. Zisopol and A. Dumitrescu, *Materiale și tehnologii primare. Aplicații practice și studii de caz*. Ploiesti, Romania: Editura Universității Petrol - Gaze din Ploiești, 2005.
- [6] D. G. Zisopol, *Ingineria valorii*. Ploiesti, Romania: Editura Universității Petrol - Gaze din Ploiești, 2004.
- [7] D. G. Zisopol and M. J. Săvulescu, *Bazele tehnologiei*. Ploiesti, Romania: Editura Universității Petrol - Gaze din Ploiești, 2003.
- [8] D. G. Zisopol, *Tehnologii industriale și de construcții, Aplicații practice și studii de caz*. Ploiesti, Romania: Editura Universității Petrol - Gaze din Ploiești, 2003.
- [9] M. J. Săvulescu, D.G. Zisopol, and I. Nae, *Bazele tehnologiei materialelor. Îndrumar de lucrări practice*. Ploiești, Romania: Editura Premier Ploiești, 1997.
- [10] M. Minescu, D. G. Zisopol, *Sudarea țevilor și fittingurilor din polietilenă de înaltă densitate*. Ploiesti, Romania: Editura Universității Petrol - Gaze din Ploiești, România, 2021.
- [11] A. Diniță, A. Neacșa, A. I. Portoacă, M. Tănase, C. N. Ilinca, and I. N. Ramadan, "Additive Manufacturing Post-Processing Treatments, a Review with Emphasis on Mechanical Characteristics," *Materials*, vol. 16, no. 13, Jan. 2023, Art. no. 4610, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma16134610>.
- [12] K. Sathish Kumar, R. Soundararajan, G. Shanthosh, P. Saravanakumar, and M. Ratteesh, "Augmenting effect of infill density and annealing on mechanical properties of PETG and CFPETG composites fabricated by FDM," *Materials Today: Proceedings*, vol. 45, pp. 2186–2191, Jan. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2020.10.078>.
- [13] D. G. Zisopol, A. I. Portoaca, I. Nae, and I. Ramadan, "A Comparative Analysis of the Mechanical Properties of Annealed PLA," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 8978–8981, Aug. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5123>.
- [14] D. G. Zisopol, I. Nae, A. I. Portoaca, and I. Ramadan, "A Statistical Approach of the Flexural Strength of PLA and ABS 3D Printed Parts," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 8248–8252, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4739>.
- [15] D. G. Zisopol, I. Nae, A. I. Portoaca, and I. Ramadan, "A Theoretical and Experimental Research on the Influence of FDM Parameters on Tensile Strength and Hardness of Parts Made of Poly(lactic Acid)," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7458–7463, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4311>.
- [16] D. G. Zisopol, M. Minescu, and D. V. Iacob, "A Theoretical-Experimental Study on the Influence of FDM Parameters on the Dimensions of Cylindrical Spur Gears Made of PLA," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 10471–10477, Apr. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5733>.
- [17] D. G. Zisopol, D. V. Iacob, and A. I. Portoaca, "A Theoretical-Experimental Study of the Influence of FDM Parameters on PLA Spur Gear Stiffness," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 9329–9335, Oct. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5183>.
- [18] A. Portoaca, I. Nae, D. G. Zisopol, and I. Ramadan, "Studies on the influence of FFF parameters on the tensile properties of samples made of ABS," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol.

- 1235, no. 1, Nov. 2022, Art. no. 012008, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/1235/1/012008>.
- [19] V. Cojocaru, D. Frunzaverde, C.-O. Miclosina, and G. Marginean, "The Influence of the Process Parameters on the Mechanical Properties of PLA Specimens Produced by Fused Filament Fabrication—A Review," *Polymers*, vol. 14, no. 5, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 886, <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym14050886>.
- [20] D. Frunzaverde *et al.*, "The Influence of the Printing Temperature and the Filament Color on the Dimensional Accuracy, Tensile Strength, and Friction Performance of FFF-Printed PLA Specimens," *Polymers*, vol. 14, no. 10, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 1978, <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym14101978>.
- [21] D. G. Zisopol, A. I. Portoaca, and M. Tanase, "Dimensional Accuracy of 3D Printed Dog-bone Tensile Samples: A Case Study," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 11400–11405, Aug. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.6060>.
- [22] D. G. Zisopol, I. Nae, and A. I. Portoaca, "Compression Behavior of FFF Printed Parts Obtained by Varying Layer Height and Infill Percentage," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 9747–9751, Dec. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5488>.
- [23] P. K. Mishra, P. Senthil, S. Adarsh, and M. S. Anoop, "An investigation to study the combined effect of different infill pattern and infill density on the impact strength of 3D printed polylactic acid parts," *Composites Communications*, vol. 24, Apr. 2021, Art. no. 100605, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coco.2020.100605>.
- [24] C.-F. Popa, M.-P. Mărghițaș, S.-V. Galațanu, and L. Marșavina, "Influence of thickness on the IZOD impact strength of FDM printed specimens from PLA and PETG," *Procedia Structural Integrity*, vol. 41, pp. 557–563, Jan. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prostr.2022.05.064>.
- [25] T. Tezel, M. Ozenc, and V. Kovan, "Impact properties of 3D-printed engineering polymers," *Materials Today Communications*, vol. 26, Mar. 2021, Art. no. 102161, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtcomm.2021.102161>.
- [26] M. A. Caminero, J. M. Chacón, I. García-Moreno, and G. P. Rodríguez, "Impact damage resistance of 3D printed continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastic composites using fused deposition modelling," *Composites Part B: Engineering*, vol. 148, pp. 93–103, Sep. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2018.04.054>.
- [27] ISO/TC 61/SC 2 Technical Committee, *ISO 179-1:2010. Plastics — Determination of Charpy impact properties — Part 1: Non-instrumented impact test*. ISO, 2010.

Malware Attack Detection in Large Scale Networks using the Ensemble Deep Restricted Boltzmann Machine

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ABSTRACT

Today, cyber attackers use Artificial Intelligence (AI) to boost the sophistication and scope of their attacks. On the defense side, AI is used to improve defense plans, robustness, flexibility, and efficiency of defense systems by adapting to environmental changes. With the developments in information and communication technologies, various exploits that are changing rapidly constitute a danger sign for cyber security. Cybercriminals use new and sophisticated tactics to boost their attack speed and size. Consequently, there is a need for more flexible, adaptable, and strong cyber defense systems that can identify a wide range of threats in real time. In recent years, the adoption of AI approaches has increased and maintained a vital role in the detection and prevention of cyber threats. This paper presents an Ensemble Deep Restricted Boltzmann Machine (EDRBM) to classify cybersecurity threats in large-scale network environments. EDRBM acts as a classification model that enables the classification of malicious flowsets in a large-scale network. Simulations were carried out to evaluate the efficacy of the proposed EDRBM model under various malware attacks. The results showed that the proposed method achieved a promising malware classification rate in malicious flowsets.

Keywords-malware; restricted Boltzmann machine; cyberthreat; deep learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the Internet has become more complex due to the increasing number of smart devices [1]. Various studies have shown that malware exploits newly discovered holes in network equipment [2]. In terms of technology, there is a fight between virus developers and network security professionals. Regarding network data, the amount of information included limits the number of countermeasures that can be implemented [3]. Although packet-level data can provide a finer level of detail, the resources required to collect them in an enterprise setting make them unfeasible to collect. This problem was addressed by introducing the concept of network flow, which provides the ability to develop algorithms that only consider specific data on network traffic [4-5]. These methods can be used to detect various security breaches. Malware is a severe threat, and its existence is one of the most difficult to detect. Vulnerable devices can be used to launch denial-of-service attacks, send spam emails, or steal sensitive data as soon as they are infected [6]. Using social engineering techniques, attackers can send email messages that entice recipients to download and install malware software [7]. Unlike other

scenarios, the victim is not required to engage with the virus, as it is installed and launched without his knowledge [8].

In a download attack, there are three stages in the infection process. At first, the attacker hopes to execute a small code (shellcode) on the target computer to gather information about the victim. To accomplish this, the attacker establishes a website that allows users to download exploit code using a drive-by download mechanism. When a victim navigates to a malicious page, the browser retrieves and executes the drive-by code [9]. When the exploit is successful, the browser executes the shellcode on the victim's computer. The shellcode executes the malware binary after downloading it (installation phase). Finally, the malware program is run (the control phase). Malicious software frequently uses a remote command and control server. Attackers can use this connection to send and receive commands, drop new executables, and steal data from the infected host [10].

A significant increase has been observed in the number of assaults against honey clients using fingerprint and obfuscation techniques to avoid detection [11]. Control phase research also focuses on identifying malicious code that has been executed

on the end host. Antivirus software may be the initial layer of security used by the vast majority of computer users around the world. Antivirus software relies primarily on signatures to detect and prevent potentially harmful apps from being executed on a computer. As malware developers adapt their code to circumvent detection, the effectiveness of antivirus software is steadily decreasing. Upon successful infection, malware distributors send commands to compromised hosts, while researchers have developed strategies to prevent further infection using signatures or reputation-based systems [12].

The Ensemble Deep Restricted Boltzmann Machine (EDRBM) is a malware detection approach for network traffic. EDRBM can distinguish between adware, ransomware, viruses, worms, trojans, and botnets in the detection process [13]. At first, EDRBM collects network flows based on the IP addresses of both parties involved in a transaction. Flowset is a term used to describe this form of aggregation. There are 441 statistical features extracted from network flow fields (for example, duration or source port) and divided into several categories. The Relative Mutual Information (RMI) metric is used to identify the most essential characteristics of software. A feature vector for a flowset, also known as a fingerprint, is created by selecting the best among the best. Using fingerprints and the random forest classifier makes it feasible to determine whether flowsets contain traffic generated by malware. This study aimed to develop an effective method for grouping flows in the network in the form of flowsets. Then statistical fingerprints are collected to preserve critical information in the flowsets.

Researchers are particularly interested in identifying and analyzing botnets. In [14], the BotHunter network infection and coordination dialogue-monitoring tool was presented, which did not rely on the C&C topology or the communication protocols of the botnet in question. In [15], a time-based behavioral analysis was presented that takes into account the duration of flows, their IP addresses, and their ports. In [16], BotSuer behavior modeling was presented to detect botnets, taking advantage of network features and performing analysis in a behavioral manner. In [17], NetFlow data was proposed to construct a host dependency model to detect botnets. According to [18], the clustering of NetFlow data can be used to detect botnets in network traffic. In [19], an invariant classification method was developed for malware behavior to identify known and previously unknown security risks. This method first bundles flows into bags and then uses statistical feature representations computed from network traffic to classify the malware. In [20], malware was detected by analyzing HTTP traffic. HTTP traffic was also examined in [21] using a clustering malware method. However, if the packet content cannot be retrieved and the malware communicates using bogus instead of standard port numbers, both methods will fail. In [22], the MalClassifier was presented to automatically categorize different malware using network traffic. In [23], Chatter was proposed, which is a similar technique to MalClassifier but requires a more fine-grained examination of packets when extracting HTTP traffic [24]. In real-world situations, both methods are less trustworthy than other techniques for malware analysis, as they depend on the order in which the network receives packets.

The proposed EDRBM introduces an effective method for grouping flows into flowsets. Unlike previous approaches that relied on time-domain attributes or port-based information, EDRBM uses statistical features from flowsets, making it more resistant to contemporary malware techniques such as port spoofing. This approach allows for the detection and differentiation of a wide range of malware types, making it a valuable contribution to cybersecurity. Overall, the EDRBM approach addresses the increasing sophistication of cyber-attackers using AI and the need for flexible and strong cyber-defense systems. Using ensemble methods and statistical features from flowsets, it provides a promising solution for real-time detection and prevention of cyber threats in complex network environments. This method uses the fingerprint as a statistical feature that depends exclusively on the number of bytes delivered during transmission [25]. To preserve user privacy, fingerprinting that is not concerned with IP addresses or ports was used, making it more resistant to port spoofing, which is commonly exploited by contemporary malware to steal identities. As fingerprints do not rely on time-domain attributes, those obtained during the evaluation are invariant for network quality and throughput, as well as for the evaluation process. Combining hundreds of flows into a flowset, information is retained such that each flow provides information on its maliciousness and other characteristics.

A good illustration of this is the grouping of flows within a specific period. Grouping rules can be defined as the IP address [26] of both the servers that make up a flow [19], which is different from the IP address of a flow. A similar approach is categorizing traffic based on source and destination IP addresses rather than the application or server function or the port being used. Unlike dividing the time domain into discrete periods and then collecting all flows within each interval, a flowset is defined by its timeout value [27]. Several techniques have been proposed to extract information from aggregated network flows, but the proposed method is the first to rely solely on the data features of network flows to detect and distinguish between a wide range of malware types. Irregularities were identified by analyzing user actions and patterns using AI. Deep learning has become the norm in research directions such as image classification, semantic segmentation, and natural language processing. In [28], the commonly used deep learning models in network attack detection, characterization, and traffic feature extraction were presented.

The proposed EDRBM model showed promising results in classifying malware flowsets, but there is not enough evidence to demonstrate how it significantly outperforms or offers unique advantages over other established methods in the field of cyber security. Further comparative analysis and benchmarks against state-of-the-art approaches are necessary to establish its novelty and superiority.

II. PROPOSED METHOD

EDRBM is used to classify unsupervised data of a probability distribution, reduce dimensionality, and extract more meaningful features. It includes connections only between visible and hidden nodes. The set of connections in hidden layers represents the probability of input data during the

training process. In the visible layer, data patterns are observed by each neuron, while the hidden layer is used to explain the patterns observed by the visible neurons. The learning rate is adjusted during the learning phase so that the model is not under or overfit. To gradually improve accuracy, the process is repeated over multiple iterations.

Every network flow between two hosts is collected during a specified amount of time, identified by their IP addresses. The timeout parameter determines the length of a flowset timeout interval and is used to determine whether an attempt to include a flow into the flowset has been successful. A flowset is generated as long as the source and destination IP addresses do not change. EDRBM extracts 441 features from each flowset, which are combined. Time, port, and data are three kinds of feature groups that can be logically organized based on the flow fields these characteristics are derived. The time group includes the inter-arrival time (the time elapsed between the timestamps of consecutive flows) and the duration of the flow. The port group contains flow fields for the source and destination ports and the protocol. This information is provided by the data group if there are many flows in a flowset, where each has a defined number of packets. When using the backing flow field-based feature, it is possible to extract several statistical characteristics for each feature group.

The underlying flow fields are represented as numeric values and then used to calculate characteristics for different time and data groups. Each collection is eventually subjected to statistical analysis to derive a variety of statistical characteristics. The group of features from the port is calculated by encoding the frequency of each flow's respective field values in one-hot form and then dividing the result by the number of flows. Statistical features are generated for each collection based on the flowset field. All statistical variables, as well as the number of different frequency values, are included in the protocol-based collection.

Collections from source or destination ports can be added as an additional statistical feature. In this collection of statistical features, the most frequent ports and the aggregated frequency of less frequently used ports were included. For each of the three feature groups, a flow subset that belongs to a flowset with the IP address it was produced, is retrieved and stored in a separate file. The only two directions that can exist simultaneously are the outgoing and arriving directions.

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Step 1: Model a large-scale network
Step 2: Cluster the domains
Step 3: Group the flow into flowsets
Step 4: Find the co-location of the domain,
        top-level unique domain names, matching
        URI path, matching files
Step 5: Estimate the fitness function
Step 6: Use EDRBM to classify the flowsets in the
        network
Step 7: Find if the classified flowsets are of
        malicious one
Step 8: Discard the malicious flowsets from the
        entire network
Step 9: End the process

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Fig. 1. Algorithm of the proposed model.

Two clusters are connected when a single file is found to be hosted by at least one element (domain) in each cluster. All clusters that contain two or more elements are considered CDNs. In the second step, malicious and benign CDNs are distinguished using a classifier trained on a small dataset of manually labeled malicious and benign clusters.

III. ENSEMBLE DEEP RESTRICTED BOLTZMANN MACHINE

It is possible to optimize the parameters of a generative model such as the RBM by utilizing stochastic gradient ascent on training data and log-likelihood. The chance of assigning a training instance (visible vector) to each hidden vector is calculated by adding up all potential hidden vectors.

$$P(v) = Z^{-1} \sum_h \exp(-E(v, h)) \quad (1)$$

The log probability derivative of a training vector about weight can be represented as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \log P(v)}{\partial w_{ij}} = \langle v_i h_j \rangle_{data} - \langle v_i h_j \rangle_{model} \quad (2)$$

The $\langle \cdot \rangle_{data}$ and $\langle \cdot \rangle_{model}$ are expected to follow their respective expected distributions, denoted by $P(h|v)$. This results in a straightforward learning strategy for stochastic gradients with the steepest ascent in a log probability:

$$P(h_j = 1|v) = \sigma(b_j + \sum_{i=1}^n v_i w_{ij}) \quad (3)$$

where the user is required to submit an initial learning rate of ϵ . As the hidden units in an RBM are not directly related to one another, it is possible to collect an unbiased sample of the data $\langle v_i h_j \rangle_{data}$. Assume a training vector in random v , where the state h_j of a hidden unit j is set to 1.

$$P(v_i = 1|h) = \sigma(a_i + \sum_{j=m}^n h_j w_{ij}), \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad (4)$$

where $r(x)$ is the logistic sigmoid function.

The same is true if there is a hidden vector h that allows to collect an unbiased data sample from the visible state. Since there are no direct connections between the visible neural units, $\langle v_i h_j \rangle_{model}$ fails to acquire an unbiased sample. To begin, the method assigns the visible unit states to a vector (training set). Equation (4) is used to compute the binary states in parallel. It is possible to construct a reconstruction of the hidden units by setting v_i to 1. This results in the weight adjustments being provided by:

$$\Delta w_{ij} = \epsilon \left(\langle v_i h_j \rangle_{data} - \langle v_i h_j \rangle_{recon} \right) \quad (5)$$

where $\langle v_i h_j \rangle_{recon}$ is the Gibbs sampling distribution.

With only one step, alternate Gibbs sampling with an initialization of the data produces a distribution of the variables. Biases a_i and b_j should be addressed using a similar learning process involving individual states. To approximate $\langle \cdot \rangle_{model}$, the study developed an alternate sampling method that included alternating Gibbs sampling cycles. This has been demonstrated to perform well enough in many significant scenarios despite approximating the log probability gradient in most cases.

A. Ensemble Classifier

This section provides a number of ways to provide ensemble RBM classifiers, motivated by their powerful representation capacity when combined with feature extraction methods. This study focused on the various ways of bagging that can be used in conjunction with RBMs because it is simple and easy to install and delivers good performance. To start, a training collection of independent instances is suggested, each represented by an input feature (X) vector and a class label with a label space value. Because of this, consider having an N -dimensional vector that includes training output as an N -dimensional matrix as input to the algorithm. For example, training instances can be considered a horizontal concatenation of two variables such as X and Y . As part of an ensemble classifier, majority voting is used to combine the output of many basic classifiers into a single result. Base classifiers can be created by combining bagging and RBMs in various ways to achieve high accuracy and diversity.

B. RMI Estimation

To avoid the curse of dimensionality, a selection process was used to identify the most informative characteristics. RMI was used to determine the relevance of these relationships. Using feature selection, it is possible to reduce computational cost and memory for storing the flowset vectors by removing the characteristics that are not useful for classification. Information exchanged between parties $MI(X, Y) = ME(Y)CE(Y|X)$, where CE is conditional entropy, ME is marginal entropy, X is the 2D flowset array, and Y is the flowset labels array. This results in $RMI(X, Y) = MI(X, Y)$. Because of the amount of memory they take up compared to all the other alternatives, these RMI scores are used to determine which features are most significant to the user.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The proposed method was trained and evaluated on malware-generated network traffic from the CTU-13 and MalRec datasets. Then, it was compared to Ensemble CNN-RNN (ECR), Ensemble CNN-DBN (ECD), Deep Neural Network (DNN), and Deep Belief Network (DBN). The performance metrics used were accuracy, precision, recall, and F-score. The scikit-learn package, Python, and C# were used on a 512 GB RAM server with 32 CPU cores.

TABLE I. DATASET SPECIFICATIONS

Dataset	Parameter	Value
Malrec	Malware recorded	66,301
	Hashing	MD5
	Network activity	PCAP form
CTU-13	Total recordings	13 captures or scenarios

The initial tests used MalRec [8], CTU-13 [22], and other publicly available datasets. The AV Class [16] malware labeling tool was used to categorize samples depending on the malware families to which they belong. To determine the top 25 families based on the highest number of samples, all samples from each family were added up and then ranked. The "other" category had a total of 24,197 malware samples, which included samples from other malware families to eliminate the need for further categorization. To identify the five most

frequent malware types, each member of the top malware families was examined to determine which kind of malware it represents. Botnet traffic from the CTU-13 dataset was also used to generate this list.

The proposed classifier was trained with 50 estimators and balanced weights to account for differences in sample sizes between different classes. RMI rates the usefulness of each feature in each feature group and assigns a score. A series of experiments were conducted, in which the number of features varied to identify the minimum characteristics required to maximize classification performance. Based on the findings, the study focused on the top five data characteristics. Port and protocol spoofing and differences in network quality were almost unaffected by the chosen feature set. After identifying these characteristics, the classification performance was analyzed for each malware species. Botnets received an F1 score of up to 94%, which was significantly higher than the random estimate for all other types of malware except ransomware. It was discovered that particular adware and ransomware samples from other categories were mislabeled. As a result, some kinds of malware might share network properties while performing malicious behavior, which is why they were classified as such. When it comes to a specific type of malware, there is nothing particularly noteworthy about these samples. The concept of a classification confidence level was used to remove samples that cannot be discriminated in different malware categories. The classification accuracy improved, but only at the expense of fewer samples being labeled as distinctive. The performance of the proposed classifier can be improved by adjusting the confidence threshold level for classifications. Certain malware requires an additional number of samples to be identified correctly.

Each type of malware has a different confidence threshold, which can be adjusted to achieve the appropriate F1 score. To avoid false positives, malware with an F1 score greater than 0.6 must be detected using thresholds such as 0.4 for adware and 0.7 for ransomware. Figure 5 shows the classification performance in terms of F1 score with a constant confidence interval between 0.5 and 0.90 for three different confidence levels. It is possible to achieve a specific level of classification confidence for a given flowset classification percentage listed in the samples column.

Fig. 2. Accuracy.

Fig. 3. Precision.

Fig. 4. Recall.

Fig. 5. F1 score.

Following the training on malware datasets, a classifier was further trained in a real-world dataset. When presented with a malware traffic sample, there was a high degree of confidence in its detection. An F1 score of 0.9 effectively reduced the total false positive rates. According to the data, there were approximately 100 adware flowsets per hour and less than 20 ransomware flowsets 20 per hour on average. It was found that worms and viruses containing similar confidence threshold

(0.7) can be found after each month, but not more than once. When the confidence level was set to 0.95, fewer than 10 instances of malicious flowsets were estimated to exist. Boltzmann machine algorithms face some limitations, such as:

- There is a problem with the adjustment of weights in the algorithm.
- For probability calculation, more time is needed for collecting statistics.
- Adjustment during simulation is a problem.
- It is significantly slower than the backpropagation method.

Adjusting the confidence threshold level for classifications can lead to better performance for certain types of malware. Different malware categories require different confidence thresholds to achieve the desired F1 score. Using appropriate confidence thresholds, the proposed classifier achieved high classification confidence for specific types of malware flowsets. The results also indicated that the proposed EDRBM model effectively reduced false-positive rates and exhibited high confidence in detecting malware traffic. This study provides insights into the performance of the classifier and the practicality of the approach in real-world scenarios. Overall, this study includes experimental findings and analyses that demonstrate the effectiveness and practicality of the EDRBM model for malware detection in network traffic. The discussion of results provides valuable insights into the performance of the classifier, the impact of confidence thresholds, and its ability to distinguish between different types of malware flowsets.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study presented the EDRBM method for classifying large-scale network cybersecurity threats. The proposed strategy exhibited remarkable performance in botnet detection and malware classifier techniques. Malicious traffic sets with rates in the 106 per-hour range were discovered on a large-scale network. This is a reasonable response given the incredibly low incidence of malware outbreaks. In contrast with several false positive alerts acknowledged by security operations centers, EDRBM accurately found minimal malicious flowsets. The simulation was carried out on two independent datasets, MalRec and CTU-13, to ensure the consistency of the model. The results showed that EDRBM detects malware with high reliability.

REFERENCES

- [1] I. H. Sarker, "Deep Cybersecurity: A Comprehensive Overview from Neural Network and Deep Learning Perspective," *SN Computer Science*, vol. 2, no. 3, Mar. 2021, Art. no. 154, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42979-021-00535-6>.
- [2] D. Chen, P. Wawrzynski, and Z. Lv, "Cyber security in smart cities: A review of deep learning-based applications and case studies," *Sustainable Cities and Society*, vol. 66, Mar. 2021, Art. no. 102655, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2020.102655>.
- [3] Z. Liu, R. Wang, N. Japkowicz, D. Tang, W. Zhang, and J. Zhao, "Research on unsupervised feature learning for Android malware detection based on Restricted Boltzmann Machines," *Future Generation Computer Systems*, vol. 120, pp. 91–108, Jul. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2021.02.015>.
- [4] K. Demertzis, L. Iliadis, E. Pimenidis, and P. Kikiras, "Variational restricted Boltzmann machines to automated anomaly detection," *Neural*

- Computing and Applications*, vol. 34, no. 18, pp. 15207–15220, Sep. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00521-022-07060-4>.
- [5] Z. E. Huma *et al.*, "A Hybrid Deep Random Neural Network for Cyberattack Detection in the Industrial Internet of Things," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 55595–55605, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3071766>.
- [6] A. Thakkar and R. Lohiya, "A Review on Machine Learning and Deep Learning Perspectives of IDS for IoT: Recent Updates, Security Issues, and Challenges," *Archives of Computational Methods in Engineering*, vol. 28, no. 4, pp. 3211–3243, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11831-020-09496-0>.
- [7] I. Bello *et al.*, "Detecting ransomware attacks using intelligent algorithms: recent development and next direction from deep learning and big data perspectives," *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*, vol. 12, no. 9, pp. 8699–8717, Sep. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12652-020-02630-7>.
- [8] C. Gupta, I. Johri, K. Srinivasan, Y. C. Hu, S. M. Qaisar, and K. Y. Huang, "A Systematic Review on Machine Learning and Deep Learning Models for Electronic Information Security in Mobile Networks," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 5, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22052017>.
- [9] A. Basit, M. Zafar, X. Liu, A. R. Javed, Z. Jalil, and K. Kifayat, "A comprehensive survey of AI-enabled phishing attacks detection techniques," *Telecommunication Systems*, vol. 76, no. 1, pp. 139–154, Jan. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11235-020-00733-2>.
- [10] S. Tsimenidis, T. Lagkas, and K. Rantos, "Deep Learning in IoT Intrusion Detection," *Journal of Network and Systems Management*, vol. 30, no. 1, Oct. 2021, Art. no. 8, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10922-021-09621-9>.
- [11] M. Veena *et al.*, "A Detection of Malware Embedded into Web Pages Using Client Honeypot," in *Computer Security Threats*, London, UK: IntechOpen, 2020.
- [12] Q. Zhuang, Y. Liu, L. Chen, and Z. Ai, "Proof of Reputation: A Reputation-based Consensus Protocol for Blockchain Based Systems," in *Proceedings of the 1st International Electronics Communication Conference*, Okinawa, Japan, Apr. 2019, pp. 131–138, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3343147.3343169>.
- [13] C. X. Zhang, J. S. Zhang, N.-N. Ji, and G. Guo, "Learning ensemble classifiers via restricted Boltzmann machines," *Pattern Recognition Letters*, vol. 36, pp. 161–170, Jan. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patrec.2013.10.009>.
- [14] G. Gu, V. Yegneswaran, M. Fong, and W. Lee, "BotHunter: Detecting Malware Infection Through IDS-Driven Dialog Correlation," in *Proceedings of the 16th USENIX Security Symposium*, Boston, MA, USA, Aug. 2007, pp. 167–182.
- [15] V. Oujezsky, T. Horvath, and V. Skorpil, "Modeling botnet C&C traffic lifespans from NetFlow using survival analysis," in *2016 39th International Conference on Telecommunications and Signal Processing (TSP)*, Vienna, Austria, Jun. 2016, pp. 50–55, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSP.2016.7760827>.
- [16] N. Kheir and C. Wolley, "BotSuer: Suing Stealthy P2P Bots in Network Traffic through Netflow Analysis," in *Cryptology and Network Security*, Paraty, Brazil, 2013, pp. 162–178, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-02937-5_9.
- [17] J. François, S. Wang, R. State, and T. Engel, "BotTrack: Tracking Botnets Using NetFlow and PageRank," in *Networking 2011*, Valencia, Spain, 2011, pp. 1–14, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-20757-0_1.
- [18] P. Amini, R. Azmi, and M. Araghizadeh, "Botnet Detection using NetFlow and Clustering," *Advances in Computer Science: an International Journal*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 139–149, Mar. 2014.
- [19] K. Bartos, M. Sofka, and V. Franc, "Optimized Invariant Representation of Network Traffic for Detecting Unseen Malware Variants," in *Proceedings of the 25th USENIX Security Symposium (USENIX Security 16)*, 2016, pp. 807–822.
- [20] R. Perdisci, W. Lee, and N. Feamster, "Behavioral clustering of HTTP-based malware and signature generation using malicious network traces," in *Proceedings of the 7th USENIX conference on Networked systems design and implementation*, San Jose, CA, USA, Dec. 2010.
- [21] M. Z. Rafique and J. Caballero, "FIRMA: Malware Clustering and Network Signature Generation with Mixed Network Behaviors," in *Research in Attacks, Intrusions, and Defenses*, Rodney Bay, St. Lucia, Oct. 2013, pp. 144–163, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-41284-4_8.
- [22] B. A. AlAhmadi and I. Martinovic, "MalClassifier: Malware family classification using network flow sequence behaviour," in *2018 APWG Symposium on Electronic Crime Research (eCrime)*, San Diego, CA, USA, Feb. 2018, pp. 1–13, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ECRIME.2018.8376209>.
- [23] A. Mohaisen, A. G. West, A. Mankin, and O. Alrawi, "Chatter: Classifying malware families using system event ordering," in *2014 IEEE Conference on Communications and Network Security*, San Francisco, CA, USA, Jul. 2014, pp. 283–291, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CNS.2014.6997496>.
- [24] W. G. Alheadary, "Controlling Employability Issues of Computing Graduates through Machine Learning-Based Detection and Identification," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 10888–10894, Jun. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5892>.
- [25] A. Alshutayri, "Fraud Prediction in Movie Theater Credit Card Transactions using Machine Learning," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 10941–10945, Jun. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5950>.
- [26] L. Bilge, D. Balzarotti, W. Robertson, E. Kirda, and C. Kruegel, "Disclosure: detecting botnet command and control servers through large-scale NetFlow analysis," in *Proceedings of the 28th Annual Computer Security Applications Conference*, Orlando, FL, USA, Sep. 2012, pp. 129–138, <https://doi.org/10.1145/2420950.2420969>.
- [27] W. Ali, G. Wang, K. Ullah, M. Salman, and S. Ali, "Substation Danger Sign Detection and Recognition using Convolutional Neural Networks," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 10051–10059, Feb. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5476>.
- [28] T. Yi, X. Chen, Y. Zhu, W. Ge, and Z. Han, "Review on the application of deep learning in network attack detection," *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, vol. 212, Art. no. 103580, Mar. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnca.2022.103580>.

Enhanced System Usability Scale using the Software Quality Standard Approach

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this paper is to improve the current System Usability Scale (SUS) and assess its applicability in the context of Learning Management Systems (LMS). The need to evaluate the usability of systems has become increasingly important in today's market, as it can have a significant impact on the user experience. In light of the COVID-19 pandemic, e-learning has become an essential tool for students, making LMS an appropriate research case study. Through a comprehensive literature review, it was discovered that SUS is the most widely used tool for evaluating system usability. However, SUS fails to satisfy some of the usability criteria outlined in ISO 9126 and ISO 9241-11. Therefore, this paper proposes an enhanced SUS model and its conceptual framework to address these limitations. The proposed model was validated using a case study approach, involving subject matter experts and software testing students, who evaluated the reliability of the enhanced SUS. Additionally, the existing and enhanced SUS models were evaluated based on an LMS case study and the results were used to calculate the enhanced SUS's reliability coefficient using Cronbach's alpha. The validation results show that the enhanced SUS has higher reliability with improved quality coverage compared to the original SUS. The proposed model has the potential to enhance the evaluation of system usability and, consequently, improve user experience.

Keywords-System Usability Scale (SAS); usability; software quality

I. INTRODUCTION

Usability refers to the ease of use and user satisfaction with a system [1]. Usability is also defined as an endeavor to quantify friendliness by measuring certain quantifiable end user

attributes, such as users' skill, time to learn, productivity from utilizing the system, and appraisal of user's engagement with the entire system [2]. In the context of Learning Management Systems (LMS), usability is crucial for effective teaching and learning. According to [3], improving the usability of LMS

interfaces can enhance student engagement and the learning outcome. Hence, it is very crucial to evaluate the usability quality of a system or software in order to provide a higher level of user satisfaction [22]. It is very important to maintain the quality of the system as it is very difficult to gain the trust of the user who has had a bad experience using a system with bad quality [4]. There are various methods that can be used in order to measure the usability score of a system [23]. One of the methods is to use the Standardized Usability Questionnaire and calculate the score based on the result. System Usability Scale (SUS) is one such standardized usability questionnaire [5] which is used to evaluate the quality of a product or system [6]. SUS was introduced by John Brooke from Digital Corporation in 1984. Since then, it has become the most widely used standardized usability questionnaire among the researchers and practitioners of usability [7]. SUS consists of ten questions which are directed to measure the usability quality of a system.

According to ISO 9241-11 [8], usability is "the extent to which a product can be used by the specified users to achieve the specified goals with effectiveness, efficiency, and satisfaction in a specified context of use". Based on ISO 9241-11, usability is defined using three criteria which are effectiveness, efficiency, and satisfaction. According to ISO 9126 [9], usability is redefined "as the capability of the software to be understood, learned, used and liked by the user when used under specified conditions". In ISO 9126, usability is defined using five criteria which are understandability, learnability, operability, attractiveness, and usability compliance. The usability criteria defined by ISO 9241-11 and ISO 9126 are shown in Table I.

TABLE I. USABILITY CRITERIA CLASSIFICATION

ISO	Usability criteria
ISO 9241-11	Efficiency
	Effectiveness
	Satisfaction
ISO 9126	Understandability
	Learnability
	Operability
	Attractiveness
	Usability compliance

These usability criteria were mapped to the questions in SUS to identify the usability criteria based on ISO 9241-11 and ISO 9126. More than one usability criteria may be mapped for each question. To map the questions and usability criteria, a conceptual model is illustrated. Figure 1 shows the conceptual model. UQ refers to the number of Usability Questions in the SUS. SUS evaluates the satisfaction of the user, the understandability of the user about the system, the learnability of the user about the system, the operability of the system, the usability compliance, and the efficiency of the system. However, SUS does not have any usability questions that evaluate the effectiveness and attractiveness of a system.

II. ENHANCED SYSTEM USABILITY SCALE

An enhanced conceptual model of the SUS and enhanced SUS questionnaire is proposed in this work. The enhanced SUS consists of 19 questions which evaluate 8 usability criteria defined using ISO 9241-11 and ISO 9126.

Fig. 1. Conceptual model of usability criteria mapped for each question in SUS.

A. The Proposed Enhanced System Usability Scale Conceptual Model

A conceptual model is proposed for the enhanced SUS. The enhanced model represents the 8 usability criteria based on ISO 9126 and ISO 9241-11. Mapping of the usability criteria and enhanced usability questions are shown in the conceptual model. Figure 2 shows the conceptual model of the usability criteria mapped for each question in the enhanced SUS. It can be seen that there are newly added 9 questions. The red bordered box represents the enhanced usability criteria and the green bordered box represents the newly added usability questions. In Figure 2, UQ14, UQ16, and UQ17 evaluate the attractiveness of the system, UQ11, UQ12, and UQ15 evaluate the effectiveness of the system, UQ5, UQ13, and UQ14 evaluate the usability compliance, and UQ18 and UQ19 evaluate, the efficiency of the system.

Fig. 2. Conceptual model of usability criteria mapped for each question in the enhanced SUS.

B. The Proposed Enhanced System Usability Scale

SUS is enhanced as the existing SUS does not evaluate the required usability criteria. Hence, the existing SUS has been

enhanced by adding 9 questions. The questions are adapted from the existing standardized usability questionnaire. Table II shows the proposed enhanced SUS. The table also shows the standardized usability questionnaire that is used as a reference.

TABLE II. ENHANCED SYSTEM USABILITY SCALE

No	Questions	Adapted
UQ1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently.	SUS [6, 7]
UQ2	I found the system unnecessarily complex.	SUS [6, 7]
UQ3	I thought the system was easy to use.	SUS [6, 7]
UQ4	I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system.	SUS [6, 7]
UQ5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated.	SUS [6, 7]
UQ6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system.	SUS [6, 7]
UQ7	I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly.	SUS [6, 7]
UQ8	I found the system very awkward to use.	SUS [6, 7]
UQ9	I felt very confident using the system.	SUS [6, 7]
UQ10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system.	SUS [6, 7]
UQ11	Tasks can be performed in a straightforward manner using this software.	SUMI [18]
UQ12	I'm unable to complete my work effectively using this system.	CSUQ [13]
UQ13	I found the interface design of the system follows the usability standards.	Question created based on ISO 9126 definition [9]
UQ14	I found this system does not fulfil the usability standards.	Question created based on ISO 9126 definition [9]
UQ15	I can use it successfully every time	USE [19]
UQ16	I found this system's color and graphical design is not attractive enough.	CSUQ [16]
UQ17	I found this system's user interface is very user friendly.	CSUQ [16]
UQ18	This system responds too slowly to inputs.	SUMI [18]
UQ19	This system helps me to do my job efficiently.	CSUQ [15]

III. METHODOLOGY

Interviews among the Subject Matter Experts (SMEs) were carried out to validate the enhanced SUS. The experts were provided with questions about the understanding of the usability and the enhanced SUS questionnaire. The example of questions that were asked to the SMEs are:

- What is your philosophy on usability?
- Do you think it is important to identify the usability score of a system?
- Do you think it is important to enhance the existing SUS?
- Do you think the enhanced SUS would improve the score and be more reliable compared to the existing SUS?
- Do you think one usability question can be mapped to more than one usability criteria?

Besides that, a survey was conducted among the students who had studied and have knowledge in software verification and validation to validate the reliability and suitability of the

questions to evaluate the usability of a system. The data obtained were used to validate the enhanced SUS. After the validation among the SMEs was completed, the data gathered were used to calculate the coefficient reliability using Cronbach's alpha.

IV. VALIDATION

The qualitative method was used to validate the relevancy of usability sub-criteria mapping with the usability questions and the reliability of the usability questions. This method was carried out among three groups of SMEs. The SMEs were Certified Testers Foundation Level (CTFL) academician experts, industrial IT experts, and computer science students studying Software Verification and Validation in UTeM (Figure 3).

Fig. 3. Flowchart of the summarised validation methods.

V. RESULT

Four IT experts and two academician experts were involved in the validation of the mapped criteria for the usability question in the enhanced SUS. The IT experts were quality assurance engineers with working experience of more than four years. The academician experts were CTFL-certified senior lecturers with working experience of more than 20 years (Table III). Each of the participants involved in this research as the SME was assigned with an ID (Table IV).

TABLE III. VALIDATION EXPERTS SUMMARY

Participants	Quantity
University	
Academician	2
Industrial (IT Experts)	
Quality Assurance (QA) Engineer	4
Total	6

TABLE IV. SME IDs

No	Category	ID
1	Academician 1	AD1
2	Academician 2	AD2
3	QA Engineer 1	QAE1
4	QA Engineer 2	QAE2
5	QA Engineer 3	QAE3
6	QA Engineer 4	QAE4

Fig. 4. SMEs agreement regarding enhancing the existing SUS.

Figure 4 shows the total percentage of the SMEs that agreed in enhancing the existing SUS. In overall, 5 out of 6 respondents, agreed to enhance the existing SUS (83%). The remaining SME had conditionally agreed. The SMEs agreed that one usability question can be mapped to more than one usability criteria and think that the enhanced SUS would improve the score and be more reliable compared to the existing SUS. Besides, the SMEs were asked about the philosophy of the usability in a system. Various explanations were given by the SMEs. AD1 emphasized learning through a system. "A system with good usability should have less learning curve and be more usable." User-friendliness is an important aspect of a system. A system must be capable enough to be used by all groups of people. Most importantly, those who doesn't have a technology background. This aspect was emphasized by two SMEs: "A system must be user-friendly to ease the end users because not all of them have technology background. As the LMS will be used by students from different fields of study, it is really important to ensure that the system performs well and is easy to use"[QAE4]. "A good usability criterion of a system is having features that are user friendly. An LMS should be easy to use and learn" [QAE2]. Lastly, time is a vital aspect when the user uses a system. A system with good usability must be able to serve the users without consuming ime. QAE1 emphasized on this aspect during the validation process: "Usability is a scale to test the usability of a system where it is easy to use or difficult for a user to use the system. User can use lesser time to learn how to use the system and can easily start using a system."

A. Verification of System Usability Scale Mapping with Usability Criteria

Based on Figure 5, all the experts have either agreed (4) or strongly agreed (5) with UQ1, UQ2, and UQ5. Meanwhile, two of the experts were neutral (3) to the criteria mapped for UQ3, UQ4, and UQ13, one of the experts rated as neutral (3) UQ6, UQ7, UQ9, UQ10, UQ11, UQ14, UQ15, UQ17, and UQ18 and three of the experts rated neutral UQ8. One expert disagreed (2) with the criteria mapped in UQ4, UQ6, UQ12, UQ14, UQ16, UQ17, UQ18, and UQ19. However, the criteria remained similar for UQ4, UQ6, UQ12, UQ14, UQ16, UQ17, UQ18, and UQ19 as only one SME disagreed with the other five.

Fig. 5. Chart analysis of the validation of the usability criteria mapped to the usability questions.

B. Validation of the Reliability of the Usability Questions in Enhanced SUS with SMEs

The SMEs were asked to evaluate the reliability and suitability of the usability questions in the enhanced SUS. Based on Figure 6, all the experts either agreed (4) or strongly agreed (5) with UQ1, UQ2, UQ3, UQ4, UQ5, UQ6, UQ7, UQ8, UQ9, and UQ10. Meanwhile, two of the experts were neutral (3) to the reliability of the questions for UQ17 and one was neutral (3) to UQ14, UQ15, and UQ19. Moreover, one SME disagreed (2) with the reliability of UQ11, UQ12, UQ13, UQ14, UQ16, and UQ18 were sustained as only one out of six SMEs disagreed with them.

Fig. 6. Chart analysis the validation of the reliability of the usability questions in the enhanced SUS.

C. Validation of the Reliability of the Usability Questions in Enhanced SUS with Software Verification and Validation Students

A survey was conducted among a group of 80 students who had studied and have knowledge of software verification and validation. They were asked to evaluate the reliability and suitability of the usability questions in the enhanced SUS.

Table V shows the outcome of the survey. None question was rejected by the respondents as the sum of agree and strongly agree was above 50% for all. The data collected were used to calculate the reliability of the enhanced SUS using the Cronbach's alpha method.

TABLE V. ANALYSIS OF VALIDATING THE RELIABILITY OF THE USABILITY QUESTIONS IN PERCENTAGE (%)

No	Strongly Disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Neutral (3)	Agree (4)	Strongly Agree (5)	Sum of (4) and (5)
UQ1	1.16%	1.16%	4.65%	30.23%	62.79%	93.02%
UQ2	1.16%	4.65%	1.16%	25.58%	56.98%	82.56%
UQ3	2.33%	3.49%	5.81%	22.10%	66.28%	88.38%
UQ4	4.65%	8.14%	6.98%	23.26%	56.78%	80.04%
UQ5	1.16%	2.33%	8.14%	29.10%	59.30%	88.40%
UQ6	3.49%	8.14%	18.6%	13.95%	55.81%	69.76%
UQ7	1.16%	1.16%	6.98%	27.91%	62.80%	90.71%
UQ8	6.98%	13.95%	15.12%	19.77%	44.19%	63.96%
UQ9	1.16%	2.33%	11.63%	31.40%	53.49%	84.89%
UQ10	2.33%	11.63%	8.14%	20.93%	56.78%	77.71%
UQ11	1.16%	3.49%	6.98%	33.72%	54.65%	88.40%
UQ12	4.65%	11.63%	13.95%	17.44%	52.33%	69.77%
UQ13	2.33%	3.49%	6.98%	32.56%	54.65%	87.21%
UQ14	4.65%	11.63%	13.95%	20.93%	48.84	69.77%
UQ15	1.16%	2.33%	12.79%	32.56%	51.16%	83.72%
UQ16	6.98%	12.79%	16.28%	19.77%	44.19%	63.96%
UQ17	1.16%	1.16%	4.65%	30.23%	62.79%	92.42%
UQ18	2.33%	10.46%	17.44%	18.60%	51.16%	69.76%
UQ19	1.16%	2.33%	11.63%	27.91%	56.98%	84.89%

D. Reliability Test

Reliability can be expressed in terms of stability, equivalence, and consistency [10]. A frequent technique is consistency check, which is also known as Cronbach's alpha coefficient. For estimating the internal consistency, only one test is required as opposed to test-retest for stability and alternate form for equivalence. Cronbach's alpha is a measurement of the squared correlation between the true and the observed scores [11, 12]. To put it another way, the ratio of true score variance to the observed score variance is used to determine dependability. The basic equation for alpha used in the calculation is:

$$a = \frac{n}{n-1} \left(1 - \frac{\sum V_i}{V_{test}} \right) \tag{1}$$

where *n* is the number of questions, *V_i* is the variance of scores on each question, and *V_{test}* is the total variance of the overall scores on the entire test.

The number of questions (items), the variance of the scores upon every item, and the variance of the overall score all play a role in calculating Cronbach's alpha. The alpha value ranges from 0 to 1. If the alpha number is higher than 0.70, the level is considered acceptable. If *V_{test}* is greater than *V_i*, then this number will be high. The scores are dispersed due to the huge volatility. Table VI shows the Cronbach's alpha rule of thumb. The Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient was calculated with the IBM SPSS Statistics software [13].

The enhanced SUS reliability coefficient was calculated based on the result obtained from the SMEs and the survey

respondents. The reliability coefficient of SUS is calculated using IBM SPSS Statistics. According to the SPSS analysis, the Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient for enhanced SUS is 0.954. Figures 7 and 8 show the case processing summary and reliability coefficient recorded from SPSS. We can see in Figure 7 that there are 86 valid cases to process and the total percentage of cases processed is 100%. According to Figure 8, the number of items evaluated is 19 and Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient is 0.954.

TABLE VI. CRONBACH'S ALPHA RULE OF THUMB

Alpha	Level of consistency
>0.9	Excellent
>0.8	Good
>0.7	Acceptable
>0.6	Questionable
>0.5	Poor
<0.5	Unacceptable

Case Processing Summary

Cases	N		%	
	Valid	Excluded ^a		
	86	0	100.0	.0
Total	86		100.0	

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Fig. 7. Case processing summary of the enhanced SUS.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.954	19

Fig. 8. Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient of the enhanced SUS.

E. Comparison of Key Properties

The reliability coefficient of the enhanced SUS is 0.95 and it is greater by 0.03 from the existing SUS. As a result from the validation of the enhanced SUS through SMEs and reliability coefficient, all the proposed usability questions are accepted, and no changes were made to the proposed questionnaire. Table VII shows the comparison of the key properties between SUSU and enhanced SUS.

TABLE VII. COMPARISON OF KEY PROPERTIES

Key Properties	SUS	Enhanced SUS
Number of questions	10	19
License type	Free	Free
Subject of evaluation	Computer software	Computer software
Reliability coefficient	0.92	0.95
Usability criteria coverage	Understandability Learnability Operability Satisfaction Efficiency Usability compliance	Understandability Learnability Operability Satisfaction Efficiency Usability compliance Attractiveness Effectiveness

VI. CONCLUSION

The proposed Enhanced System Usability Scale was validated in this paper in terms of reliability coefficient and the usability criteria that it covers. It is vital to ensure that all the usability criteria are evaluated while validating or evaluating the usability of a system. However, future enhancement can be made by reducing the number of questions as most of the users prefer to spend less time evaluating a system's usability.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. Hafeez, S. Javed, A. B. Murtaza, A. Aziz, S. M. Hassan, and I. Hussain, "A Survey on the Adaption of CMS in Pakistani Universities," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 5037–5040, Dec. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3159>.
- [2] S. Vairamuthu and S. M. Anuncia, "Reconnoitering Students' Satisfaction of an Online Based Assessment System to Improve Usability using PSO: An Examination into a Problem Solving and Programming Course," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 6, no. 5, pp. 1207–1211, Oct. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.800>.
- [3] M. Jordan and N. Duckett, "Universities Confront 'Tech Disruption': Perceptions of Student Engagement Online Using Two Learning Management Systems," *The Journal of Public and Professional Sociology*, vol. 10, no. 1, Jan. 2018.
- [4] I. Maslov, S. Nikou, and P. Hansen, "Exploring user experience of learning management system," *The International Journal of Information and Learning Technology*, vol. 38, no. 4, pp. 344–363, Jan. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJILT-03-2021-0046>.
- [5] ISO/TC 159/SC 4 Ergonomics of human-system interaction Technical Committee, *ISO 9241-11:1998. Ergonomic requirements for office work with visual display terminals (VDTs) — Part 11: Guidance on usability*. Geneva, Switzerland: ISO, 1998.
- [6] J. R. Lewis and J. Sauro, "Revisiting the Factor Structure of the System Usability Scale," *JUX - The Journal of User Experience*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 183–192, Aug. 2017.
- [7] J. R. Lewis, "The System Usability Scale: Past, Present, and Future," *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, vol. 34, no. 7, pp. 577–590, Jul. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10447318.2018.1455307>.
- [8] ISO/TC 159/SC 4 Technical Committee, *ISO 9241-11:2018. Ergonomics of human-system interaction*. Geneva, Switzerland: ISO, 2018.
- [9] ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 7 Technical Committee, *ISO/IEC 9126-1:2001. Software engineering — Product quality — Part 1: Quality model*. Geneva, Switzerland: ISO, 2001.
- [10] R. Reh, M. L. Mursidi, and N. A. A. Husin, "Reliability analysis for pilot survey in integrated survey management system," in *2011 Malaysian Conference in Software Engineering*, Johor Bahru, Malaysia, Sep. 2011, pp. 220–222, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MySEC.2011.6140673>.
- [11] J. M. Cortina, "What is coefficient alpha? An examination of theory and applications," *Journal of Applied Psychology*, vol. 78, no. 1, pp. 98–104, 1993, <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.78.1.98>.
- [12] N. Schmitt, "Uses and abuses of coefficient alpha," *Psychological Assessment*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 350–353, 1996, <https://doi.org/10.1037/1040-3590.8.4.350>.
- [13] J. R. Lewis, "IBM computer usability satisfaction questionnaires: Psychometric evaluation and instructions for use," *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 57–78, Jan. 1995, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10447319509526110>.
- [14] J. Sauro and J. R. Lewis, "Chapter 8 - Standardized Usability Questionnaires," in *Quantifying the User Experience*, J. Sauro and J. R. Lewis, Eds. Boston, MA, USA: Morgan Kaufmann, 2012, pp. 185–240.
- [15] L. Buenafior, "ISO 9126 Software Quality Characteristics," *Medium*, Sep. 02, 2017. <https://medium.com/@leanardbuenafior/iso-9126-software-quality-characteristics-a25a26e7d046>.
- [16] Sholiq, R. A. Auda, A. P. Subriadi, A. Tjahyanto, and A. D. Wulandari, "Measuring software quality with usability, efficiency, and portability characteristics," *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, vol. 704, no. 1, Nov. 2021, Art. no. 012039, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/704/1/012039>.
- [17] O. A. Rotaru, S. Vert, R. Vasiiu, and D. Andone, "Standardised Questionnaires in Usability Evaluation. Applying Standardised Usability Questionnaires in Digital Products Evaluation," in *Information and Software Technologies*, Cham, 2020, pp. 39–48, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-59506-7_4.
- [18] J. Kirakowski and M. Corbett, "SUMI: the Software Usability Measurement Inventory," *British Journal of Educational Technology*, vol. 24, no. 3, pp. 210–212, 1993, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8535.1993.tb00076.x>.
- [19] J. Kirakowski and M. Corbett, "SUMI: the Software Usability Measurement Inventory," *British Journal of Educational Technology*, vol. 24, no. 3, pp. 210–212, 1993, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8535.1993.tb00076.x>.
- [20] R. A. Ali and M. R. M. Arshad, "Perspectives of Students' Behavior Towards Mobile Learning (M-learning) in Egypt: an Extension of the UTAUT Model," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 1109–1114, Aug. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.710>.
- [21] M. Hemmati and H. Hosseini, "Effect of IT Application on Project Performance Focusing on the Mediating Role of Organizational Innovation, Knowledge Management and Organizational Capabilities," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 6, no. 6, pp. 1221–1226, Dec. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.769>.
- [22] N. A. Kamarudin, R. R. Raja Ikram, F. N. Azman, S. S. Syed Ahmad, and D. Bin Zainuddin, "A Study of The Effects of Short-Term AI Coding Course with Gamification Elements on Students' Cognitive Mental Health," *TEM Journal*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 1854–1862, Nov. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.18421/TEM114-53>.
- [23] Y. Thamilarasan and R. R. R. Ikram, "MyMUET: A Design of a Mobile based Crowdsourced Assessment for Malaysia University English Test with Non-Synchronous Participant Interaction," *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering*, vol. 8, no. 11, Sep. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.35940/ijitee.K2277.0981119>.

The Effect of Iron Content on the Thermodynamic Properties of Syndiotactic Polypropylene/Iron Composites

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the influence of iron concentration on the thermodynamic properties of syndiotactic polypropylene (sPP)/iron composites in the melt phase in a series of samples with varying iron content, ranging from 0 to 10% with a step of 2%. The HYSYS software was used to estimate molecular weight, critical temperature (T_c), critical volume (V_c), and eccentricity (E_c). The results showed that all these properties changed as the iron content varied. The findings of this study confirmed that iron concentration has an impact on the mechanical and chain dynamic (microscopic) properties of polymer composites.

Keywords-polymer composites; thermodynamic properties; HYSYS; critical temperature; critical pressure; molecular weight; eccentricity

I. INTRODUCTION

Polymer composites have been known to have superior mechanical, thermal, and physical properties compared to polymers [1-6]. These characteristics change as the reinforcement phase changes [7-13]. Since polymer composites do not follow the same corrosion mechanisms as iron and steel, they are quickly replacing these materials. Due to these characteristics, polymer composites are versatile in many industrial applications, and their study has attracted much attention over the past few decades [3]. Fillers, such as iron content, clay, etc., alter not only the macrostructure properties of polymer composites but also their properties at the molecular level (microstructure properties) [17-20]. The thermal properties of polymer composites vary with the dose of the reinforcing phase [19].

Several studies have investigated syndiotactic polypropylene (sPP) composites. In [14], the rheological characteristics of sPP were studied, examining how the syndiotacticity of polypropylene affected the rheological characteristics, including the plateau modulus and entanglement molecular weight. When the syndiotacticity of sPP increased, a rise in the plateau modulus was observed. However, many polymers and polymer composite systems

have not yet undergone such investigation. In [15], the rheological, thermodynamic, and multilayered film properties were studied on polyethylene oxide and montmorillonite clay, showing that an increase in the clay concentration caused a progressive increase in the storage and loss moduli. The thermal properties of composites and films were investigated using DSC and TGA, relating them to their microstructural characteristics, but without examining the relationship between molecular weight and other thermodynamic parameters, such as critical temperature, critical volume, and molecular weight.

In [16], it was examined how clay levels affect rheological variables, such as plateau modulus and entanglement molecular weight. Chinese bentonite clay was used to create clay and polypropylene composites, showing that increasing the clay concentration increased the plateau modulus and, as a result, lowered the entanglement molecular weight. In [18], the impact of thermodynamic variables on wood/plastic composites was studied. Plastics were melted at 180°C to prepare the composites, which were then dispensed onto wooden surfaces. When correlating the contact angle with the wood content, it was discovered that the contact angle decreased. At the polymer/wood interface, it was discovered that sanding results in decreased surface free energy and higher interfacial shear strengths. At higher temperatures, composite wetting was

caused by polymer characteristics rather than interfacial tension at the polymer/wood contact. In [19], the thermal properties of sPP/iron composites were investigated by examining how the iron content affected thermal characteristics such as melting point, crystallization temperature, and glass transition temperature. The results showed that an increase in iron content affected thermal properties, such as melting point, crystallization, and glass transition temperatures, but this study did not assess how iron content affects thermodynamic properties, such as critical temperatures, critical volumes, molecular weights, and eccentricities.

Several studies have investigated the synthesis, thermal, and rheological investigation of polymers and composites made of polymers and iron. However, there is a lack of studies on the thermodynamic properties of sPP/iron composites or even estimation using software. As a result, this study investigated the relationship between the iron content and the thermodynamic characteristics of sPP/iron composites. Furthermore, this study estimated the thermodynamic properties of sPP/iron composites using HYSYS software, expanding previous studies [16, 19].

II. METHODOLOGY

Thermodynamic properties such as critical temperature (T_c), critical volume (V_c), molecular weight, and eccentricity (E_c) were calculated for sPP/iron composites with varying iron loadings ranging from 0 to 10% with a step size of 2%. The library components of the HYSYS software do not contain pure polymers and polymer/iron composites, but the simulation foundation manager allows for the creation of hypothetical components. If HYSYS is given two of the three base properties (molecular weight, normal boiling point, and density), it can estimate the critical temperature, critical volume, and eccentricity. To estimate the undetermined attributes, an estimation approach was used before installing the hypothetical components. This study used the default approach [21]. Les-Kesler, Bergman, and Cavett are three approaches that are accessible for the estimation of the critical temperature and other thermodynamic parameters. When choosing the default method, HYSYS selects according to the supplied data [22]. HYSYS chose the Pitzer approach to determine critical volume and eccentricity [23].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents results and a discussion of the effect of iron content on the thermodynamic properties of sPP/iron composites, examining critical temperature, critical pressure, critical volume, eccentricity, and molecular weight as a function of iron content, and finding that it greatly affects the thermodynamic properties of polymer composites.

A. Effect of Iron Content on Critical Temperature

The results showed that iron content is positively correlated with critical temperature. To reach the critical point, more energy is needed as the critical temperature rises, showing that composites made of sPP and iron have greater thermal strength. Figure 1 shows the connection between iron content and critical temperatures, pointing out that an increase in iron content improves thermal stability, and increases the

intermolecular forces and the mechanical strength of sPP/iron composites. Previous studies [16, 19] confirm these two conclusions. The link between plateau modulus and clay concentrations was investigated in [16]. The plateau modulus, also known as the elastic modulus, demonstrates how the sPP/clay composites react mechanically. Composites made of sPP and clay with larger clay concentrations have higher plateau moduli and critical temperatures, showing that adding clay and iron to the filler increases thermal and mechanical strength. When the critical temperatures and melting points of the sPP/iron composites are matched, thermal stability is confirmed. Figure 2 illustrates the connection between the critical temperature and melting point temperatures, showing the increased critical and melting temperatures of sPP/iron composites with more iron content.

Fig. 1. Relationship between critical temperature and iron content of sPP/iron composites.

Fig. 2. Relationship between melting point temperature and iron content of sPP/iron composites.

B. Effect of Iron Content on Molecular Weight

According to Figure 3, there is a correlation between simulated molecular weight (Mw) values and the amount of iron in sPP/iron composites. The graph shows how the molecular weight of the sPP/iron composites increases as the iron content increases. The molecular weight of polymer and polymer composites influences how quickly they relax [24]. These results can be further confirmed by [17], by matching the cross-over frequency of the master curves (relaxation time) and simulated molecular weights of the polymer composites.

Polymer composites of higher filler content have higher relaxation time and molecular weights.

Fig. 3. Relationship between molecular weight and iron content of sPP/iron composites.

C. Effect of Iron Content on Critical Volume

Critical volume is based on the volume of the material observed [25]. The critical volume was estimated for each sPP/iron sample. Figure 4 shows the connection between critical volume and iron concentrations, pointing out that an increase in iron concentration increases critical volume, which is consistent with [25].

Fig. 4. Relationship between critical volume and iron content of sPP/iron composites.

D. Effect of Iron Contents on Eccentricity

Eccentricity is a metric for the way the crystals or monomers of a material are organized [26]. The eccentricity of all sPP/iron composites was simulated. Figure 5 shows the correlation between eccentricity and iron concentrations, demonstrating that eccentricity increased with increasing iron content. This might have something to do with how iron content affects crystallinity and, therefore, the eccentricity of sPP/iron composites. This finding can be further verified from the melting points of sPP/iron composites. Polymer composites with a higher iron content have higher melting points, indicating that the monomers are organized more consistently and hence require more energy to melt.

Fig. 5. Relationship between eccentricity and iron content of sPP/iron composites.

These results show how the iron content affects the thermodynamic properties of sPP/iron composites. An increase in iron content increased the critical temperature and altered other thermodynamic parameters. This is because an increase in iron content increases the strength and thermal stability of sPP/iron composites, as more energy is required to reach the critical temperature. Figure 2 shows the relationship between the melting point and the iron content, demonstrating that the melting point of sPP/iron composites increases with increasing iron content. This indicates that the iron content affects the intermolecular forces of the sPP/iron composites. It can be concluded that iron content affects the molecular architecture of sPP/iron composites, and hence their thermal and microstructure properties.

IV. CONCLUSION

Thermodynamic analysis provides wide information about the properties of materials, as it provides information both at the macromolecular and molecular levels. This study demonstrates that the iron content affects not only the other properties but also the thermodynamic properties of sPP/iron composites. Thermodynamic properties were determined using the HYSYS software, and these properties were analyzed as functions of the iron content. The critical temperature, critical volume, molecular weight, and eccentricity were found to increase with increasing iron content, reflecting the fact that iron content affects the polymer chain at both macromolecular and molecular levels. The results of this study reveal that thermodynamic information can be used to predict both the molecular and macromolecular properties of any polymer or polymer composite.

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REFERENCES

- [1] D. J. Arriola, E. M. Carnahan, P. D. Hustad, R. L. Kuhlman, and T. T. Wenzel, "Catalytic Production of Olefin Block Copolymers via Chain Shuttling Polymerization," *Science*, vol. 312, no. 5774, pp. 714–719, May 2006. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1125268>.

- [2] V. C. Gibson, "Shuttling Polyolefins to a New Materials Dimension," *Science*, vol. 312, no. 5774, pp. 703–704, May 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1127258>.
- [3] A. Ghanbari, M. C. Heuzey, P. J. Carreau, and M. T. Ton-That, "Morphological and rheological properties of PET/clay nanocomposites," *Rheologica Acta*, vol. 52, no. 1, pp. 59–74, Jan. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00397-012-0667-1>.
- [4] G. K. Jatav, R. Mukhopadhyay, and N. De, "Characterization of Swelling Behavior of Nanoclay Composite," *International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology*, vol. 2, no. 5, pp. 1560–1563, May 2013.
- [5] M. Doi, S. F. Edwards, and S. F. Edwards, *The Theory of Polymer Dynamics*. Oxford, UK: Clarendon Press, 1988.
- [6] L. J. Fetters, D. J. Lohse, D. Richter, T. A. Witten, and A. Zirkel, "Connection between Polymer Molecular Weight, Density, Chain Dimensions, and Melt Viscoelastic Properties," *Macromolecules*, vol. 27, no. 17, pp. 4639–4647, Aug. 1994, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ma00095a001>.
- [7] A. Eckstein *et al.*, "Determination of Plateau Moduli and Entanglement Molecular Weights of Isotactic, Syndiotactic, and Atactic Polypropylenes Synthesized with Metallocene Catalysts," *Macromolecules*, vol. 31, no. 4, pp. 1335–1340, Feb. 1998, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ma971270d>.
- [8] J. M. Carella, W. W. Graessley, and L. J. Fetters, "Effects of chain microstructure on the viscoelastic properties of linear polymer melts: polybutadienes and hydrogenated polybutadienes," *Macromolecules*, vol. 17, no. 12, pp. 2775–2786, Dec. 1984, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ma00142a059>.
- [9] S. Bagheri-Kazemabad *et al.*, "Morphology, rheology and mechanical properties of polypropylene/ethylene-octene copolymer/clay nanocomposites: Effects of the compatibilizer," *Composites Science and Technology*, vol. 72, no. 14, pp. 1697–1704, Sep. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2012.06.007>.
- [10] M. Sarkar, K. Dana, S. Ghatak, and A. Banerjee, "Polypropylene-clay composite prepared from Indian bentonite," *Bulletin of Materials Science*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 23–28, Feb. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12034-008-0005-5>.
- [11] Y. Xiang, Z. Peng, and D. Chen, "A new polymer/clay nano-composite hydrogel with improved response rate and tensile mechanical properties," *European Polymer Journal*, vol. 42, no. 9, pp. 2125–2132, Sep. 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurpolymj.2006.04.003>.
- [12] C. Liu, J. He, E. van Ruymbeke, R. Keunings, and C. Bailly, "Evaluation of different methods for the determination of the plateau modulus and the entanglement molecular weight," *Polymer*, vol. 47, no. 13, pp. 4461–4479, Jun. 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymer.2006.04.054>.
- [13] J. D. Ferry, *Viscoelastic Properties of Polymers*. New York, NY, USA: John Wiley & Sons, 1980.
- [14] N. Ahmad, R. Di Girolamo, F. Auriemma, C. De Rosa, and N. Grizzuti, "Relations between Stereoregularity and Melt Viscoelasticity of Syndiotactic Polypropylene," *Macromolecules*, vol. 46, no. 19, pp. 7940–7946, Oct. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ma401469a>.
- [15] S. Y. Gu, J. Ren, and Q. F. Wang, "Rheology of poly(propylene)/clay nanocomposites," *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, vol. 91, no. 4, pp. 2427–2434, 2004, <https://doi.org/10.1002/app.13403>.
- [16] N. Ahmad and E. Fouad, "Influence of Clay Contents on Rheology of Syndiotactic Polypropylene/Clay Composites," *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering*, vol. 42, no. 4, pp. 1537–1543, Apr. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13369-016-2389-7>.
- [17] N. Ahmad, E. Fouad, and F. Ahmad, "Effect of Shear Flow on Crystallization of Syndiotactic Polypropylene/Clay Composites," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 3108–3112, Aug. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2079>.
- [18] P. Rezaee Niaraki and A. Krause, "Correlation between physical bonding and mechanical properties of wood-plastic composites: part 2: effect of thermodynamic factors on interfacial bonding at wood-polymer interface," *Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology*, vol. 34, no. 7, pp. 756–768, Apr. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1080/01694243.2019.1689628>.
- [19] A. Z. Al-Khazaal and N. Ahmad, "A Study of the Impact of Iron Content on the Thermal Response of the sPP/Fe Composites," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 8555–8558, Jun. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4884>.
- [20] N. Ahmad, F. Ahmad, and I. Alenezi, "Influence of Starch Content on the Thermal and Viscoelastic Properties of Syndiotactic Polypropylene/Starch Composites," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 7228–7232, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4161>.
- [21] D. C. Cruz-Forero, O. A. González-Ruiz, and L. J. López-Giraldo, "Calculation of thermophysical properties of oils and triacylglycerols using an extended constituent fragments approach," *CT&F-Ciencia, Tecnología y Futuro*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 67–82, 2012.
- [22] C. Li, W. Jia, and X. Wu, "Application of Lee-Kesler equation of state to calculating compressibility factors of high pressure condensate gas," *Energy Procedia*, vol. 14, pp. 115–120, Jan. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2011.12.904>.
- [23] Z. Bakher and M. Kaddami, "Thermodynamic properties and Pitzer parameter determination for orthophosphoric acid from freezing point and isopiestic measurement data," *Brazilian Journal of Chemical Engineering*, vol. 35, pp. 1153–1162, 2018.
- [24] W. Thimm, C. Friedrich, M. Marth, and J. Honerkamp, "An analytical relation between relaxation time spectrum and molecular weight distribution," *Journal of Rheology*, vol. 43, no. 6, pp. 1663–1672, 1999.
- [25] B. J. Taylor and M. B. Maple, "Formula for the critical temperature of superconductors based on the electronic density of states and the effective mass," *Physical review letters*, vol. 102, no. 13, 2009, Art. no. 137003.
- [26] M. F. M. Fahmy and O. A. Farghal, "Eccentricity-based design-oriented model of fiber-reinforced polymer-confined concrete for evaluation of load-carrying capacity of reinforced concrete rectangular columns," *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, vol. 35, no. 23, pp. 1734–1758, Dec. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0731684416667239>.

Distribution of Benefits and Risks in Inter-Basin Water Transfers: The Case Study of NCT I from Upper Tana Basin to Nairobi City

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ABSTRACT

Inter-Basin Water Transfers (IBWTs) introduce complex socioeconomic, hydrological, ecological, and institutional impacts that are instrumental to decision-making. However, since most studies focus on the hydrological and ecological aspects of IBWTs for the development of sustainable water resources, it is necessary to investigate the distribution of risks (costs) and benefits of IBWTs among stakeholders. This study aimed to identify and categorize stakeholders, their relationships, and the distribution of risks/costs and benefits in the Northern Collector Tunnel phase I (NCT 1) IBWT using a stakeholder analysis method. The Athi Water Works Development Agency (AWWDA) and the Ministry of Water and Irrigation (MoWI) played a central role in the project. However, most stakeholders found the devolved units Water Services Providers (WSPs), Water Resources Authority (WRA), Water Resources Users Associations (WRUAs), and Murang'a County as the most critical institutions. Public participation in NCT1 was not inclusive but only done to meet the statutory project requirements. Significant risks of the project emerged, such as reduced river flows, drying of the springs, and Murang'a residents' ability to meet their water needs. Therefore, it is necessary to compensate for diverted water through a water levy to cover environmental externalities and catchment conservation. The increase in water supply for Nairobi City was perceived as the main benefit for the recipient basin, but an improved water levy with adequate cross-subsidies was pointed out as an instrument to catalyze water savings by the urban water utility.

Keywords-benefits; inter-basin; risks; stakeholder analysis; water allocation

I. INTRODUCTION

Water demand is increasing in many parts of the world while the available freshwater resources remain constant, especially in regions with rapid economic development and

high population growth. Arguably, these regions are often cities, which become strategic regions politically. Thus, when the water demand exceeds the supply, the solution is often supply-oriented strategies [1]. Some of the approaches have been Inter-Basin Water Transfers (IBWTs) from regions

deemed to have "surplus" water resources. By hydraulically connecting two or more river basins, a new dependency between communities is created, evoking the interests of different groups of stakeholders [2]. Consequently, some IBWT systems face resistance from local communities in the donor basin [2-6]. Unlike dams, where in 2000 the World Commission on Dams (WCD) proposed a framework to equitably share benefits [7], IBWTs have no such explicit provisions and may be complex, especially when the donor and recipient basins are in different administrative units.

NCT 1 is expected to transfer 140,000 m³/day from the Upper Tana basin in Murang'a County to Nairobi City in the Athi basin [8]. The project was financed by the World Bank and the French Development Agency (AFD) through MoWI and implemented by AWWDA. The project faced some resistance from Muranga County residents during its construction stage, as it raised concerns that their water resources would be diverted to Nairobi without tangible benefits. There is consensus among scholars that IBWT systems introduce both benefits and risks that are different between different stakeholders [2, 9-10]. Although this issue has attracted much attention, there is limited scientific research on the distribution of benefits and risks among water users/stakeholders in IBWTs. Most studies have focused on the biophysical and ecological impacts of IBWTs [11-14]. This study aims to investigate the distribution of benefits and risks in IBWTs through a stakeholder analysis in the NCT 1 project in Kenya, aiming to (i) identify and categorize stakeholders with their roles and interests, and (ii) investigate the distribution of benefits and risks among them in NCT 1.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Study Area

This study was carried out in the Upper Tana basin located in Muranga County, Kenya, which has served as a source of water for Nairobi City since the 1950s [8]. The study focused on the stakeholders who played a role and/or were affected by NCT 1. In 2012, AWWDA conducted a master plan for the development of water sources for Nairobi City and its satellite towns, recommending NCT 1 as a viable water source. AWWDA, through MoWI, obtained funding of approximately KES 6.8 billion (US 65 million) from the World Bank and AFD to implement NCT 1. The project involved a 12 km concrete tunnel, 3 m in diameter, from the Maragua, Gikigie, and Irati rivers to the Thika dam for use in Nairobi City [15].

B. Data and Methods

This study used stakeholder analysis that involved (i) identifying and (ii) categorizing stakeholders and (iii) investigating their benefits and risks following the guidelines in [16-18], adjusted to the study case. Figure 1 shows the process that involved a literature review, snowball sampling, semi-structured interviews, and a Focused Group Discussion (FGD) to identify and categorize stakeholders. Qualitative content analysis was used to identify the benefits and risks of the project for stakeholders [17, 19-21]. Initially, stakeholders were identified through a review of policy documents, project design reports, and academic papers derived from various government websites and personal communication. The interviewees were

asked to mention and provide contacts to other possible stakeholders relevant to NCT 1. Semi-structured interviews were conducted to identify the roles, relationships, benefits, and risks of stakeholders in the project using an interview guide. Additionally, an FGD was held to gather additional in-depth information on the topics. In total, 25 interviews and an FGD were conducted with a representative of the identified stakeholders. Data collection was carried out in February, March, and April of 2023.

C. Data Analysis

The interviews were analyzed with the Nvivo software, commonly referred to as software-assisted Qualitative Content Analysis (QCA). This method follows a guideline to ensure an objective interpretation of qualitative data that is primarily in text format [20, 22-23]. The stakeholders were classified according to their level of importance-influence matrix to illustrate the power interactions of the stakeholders [17]. Furthermore, in terms of benefits and risks, the interview data were coded in Nvivo and themes were developed from the research questions.

Fig. 1. Methodology steps for undertaking stakeholder analysis in the NCT 1 project, Upper Tana Basin, Kenya.

III. RESULTS

A. Stakeholder Identification and Roles in NCT 1

Figure 2 and Table I show the identified 7 categories of 27 stakeholders that have a role in NCT 1. MoWI with the support of the World Bank and AFD oversaw the financing of the project under the Water and Sanitation Service Improvement Project (WaSSIP) additional financing investment loan. The Water Sector Trust Fund (WSTF) was not involved in the NCT 1 project however, it funded the WRUAs for catchment conservation measures in Aberdares Forest. The WRA oversaw water allocation by issuing water abstraction permits for the Maragua, Gikigie, and Irati rivers. AWWDA was the implementing stakeholder in charge of design and construction. There were three Water Services Providers (WSPs) in the study area: Kahuti Water & Sanitation Company (KAWASCO), Muranga South Water & Sanitation Company (MUSWASCO), and Muranga Water & Sanitation Company (MUWASCO). Although WSPs play an important role in water provision, they were not actively involved. There were two WRUAs in the study area, Upper and Lower Maragua, formed in 2015. The involvement of WRUAs and the community was also limited, and they considered the project political. The National Environment Management Authority (NEMA) oversaw the licensing of NCT 1 to ensure environmental protection. The Murang'a County government's role was to ensure the sustainability of the project in terms of sharing benefits and

eliminating environmental risks. Although meetings were held between Muranga County government officials and AWWDA, resulting in a consensus agreement, the sitting administration,

which came to office in August 2022 was not involved in the project at the time. Most of the other stakeholders had supportive and/or informative roles.

Fig. 2. Stakeholder identification and categorization in the NCT 1 Project, Upper Tana Basin, Kenya

B. Stakeholder Characterization based on an Importance-Influence Matrix

Figure 3 illustrates the stakeholders on a 2x2 importance-influence matrix, showing those who were likely to be affected by the project (importance) and those whose decisions affected the direction of the project but were not necessarily affected by it (influence). WRA, AWWDA, and Muranga County were classified as key players. AWWDA had the power and influence to make decisions in the NCT 1 project as it was the implementing agent. Muranga County was a key player in the donor basin because it was able to influence the design review of the project to abstract flood water and lobby for the development of off-shoot water supply projects for local communities. To abstract water from the three rivers, the project had to obtain water abstraction permits from the WRA, thus it was a key player in the project. MoWI, NEMA, and Media and International donors were classified as context setters, as their decisions affected the direction of the project, although they were least affected by the impact of their decisions. WSPs, youth and women, chiefs, and consumers such as KTDA and KENGEN were classified as "subjects" because they were the most likely stakeholders to be affected by the project, but their power in decision-making was limited.

KFS, CFA, Rhino Ark, and TNC were classified as external stakeholders because they had little interest and were also not affected by the project. However, they influenced aspects of the project through funding catchment conservation activities.

Fig. 3. Stakeholders' position based on their level of importance and influence in the Upper Tana NCT I Project, Kenya.

TABLE I. STAKEHOLDERS' ROLES BASED ON THEIR MANDATE AND EXPERTISE

Stakeholder	Role/Mandate
MoWI	Support the acceleration of water reforms. Mobilize resources for the sustainable development and management of water resources.
WSTF	Provide grants to manage and develop water services in marginalized areas. Provide funds to WRUAs for catchment conservation activities.
Water Resources Authority - Upper Tana	Regulate and authorize the NCT I water transfer project.
Water Services Regulatory Board	Approve tariffs and license water service providers.
AWWDA	Develop the NCT 1 project infrastructure along with the treatment plans.
NEMA	Issuance of NEMA certificate and supervise the project on environmental issues through the Muranga office.
KFS	Conservation of the Aberdare water towers through the Gatara Forest Station.
Muranga County	Represent Muranga residents on environmental and water resources concerns.
MUSWASCO	Provide water and sanitation services to Kandara, Kigumo, and Muranga South sub-county.
MUWASCO	Provide water and sanitation services to Muranga town and its environs.
KAWASCO	Provide water and sanitation services to Kangema and Kahuro sub-counties.
Kengen (Wanjji and Mescio hydropower station)	Hydropower generation using Mathioya and Maragua rivers.
Kenya Tea Development Authority (KTDA)	Small-scale tea farmers' company.
Chiefs and Commissioners	Support the project through liaising with the community for any concerns.
NWSC	Provide water and sanitation services to Nairobi County residents.
Rhino Ark Foundation	Provide funds/grants for Aberdare water towers conservation activities through collaboration with KFS.
WRUAs - Upper and Lower Maragua catchments	To authorize the abstraction of water from the Maragua, Irati, and Gikigie rivers for NCT 1. Collaborate with WRA in illegal abstractions monitoring. Collaborate with WSTF for the conservation of the catchment.
CFA	Assist KFS in planting trees and scouting services.
World Bank & AFD	Provide credit facility for NCT 1 Project.
Consultants & Contractors	Design and construction supervision of the NCT 1 project components.
Media	Provide information on the project.
TNC - Upper Tana Nairobi Water Fund	Support water and soil conservation measures.

C. Perceived Benefits and Risks

1) Risks

There was a consensus among stakeholders on the risks of reduced flows in the rivers or the viability of the project if they abstract flood waters. To ensure adequate water supply, residents were promised off-shoot community water supply projects. However, the projects did not target areas that were adversely affected by water shortages in the county and several of the projects have not been completed, so residents still face

severe water shortage. Furthermore, some of the off-shoot community water projects became a source of water conflict with WSPs. Increasing water demand in both the donor and recipient basins and climate variability are predicted to reduce water levels in the rivers, thus continued diversion may lead to over-abstraction. Therefore, the Aberdare Forest needed to be conserved to ensure sustained flows to the rivers. However, the NCT 1 project does not have a plan or a budget for conservation activities. AWWDA acknowledged the importance of the preservation and restoration of Aberdare Forest, however, noted that it was not within their mandate but that of the KFS. Another risk was future abstractions for Muranga residents, in addition to the drying of springs and wells along the tunnel during the construction period. AWWDA constructed six monitoring wells (piezometric boreholes) in 2016 to monitor changes in groundwater flows. However, the analysis has not been conducted and therefore no information has been shared to date with the communities.

2) Benefits

There was a consensus that NCT 1 would increase the water supply to Nairobi residents. Furthermore, locals were employed in Muranga County during the construction phase of the project. Spoil from the tunnel was used to improve weathered roads and provide better access to the community. However, most of the stakeholders in the donor basin did not see the benefits of the project and advocated for part of the money from the water bills to be returned to the basin to invest in water for domestic and agricultural use and conservation measures. Based on a similar process in the Karimenu Dam in Kiambu County, Kenya, 15% of the water fees go to operation and maintenance and 75% to loan repayment, leaving only 10% for water abstraction permits and conservation activities. Furthermore, the price of abstracting raw water was KES 0.5/m³ (0.0047 USD) compared to the opportunity cost of KES 45/m³ (0.43 USD) if the water was used for agricultural activities in Murang'a County [15]. The regulation of raw water abstraction is a standard fee for all water abstractors, whether it is for small-scale agriculture or urban water supply, and there are no special provisions for IBWTs.

IV. DISCUSSION

The current study identified different categories of stakeholders and their roles in the NCT 1 project. MoWI and AWWDA played an active role, as they were the promoters of the project. WSPs and WRUAs had a high interest in the project, although their involvement was limited. Similarly, although official documents show that an agreement was signed between the AWWDA and the Murang'a County government back in 2015, the current administration had a limited role in the project. Most of the stakeholders in the Upper Tana basin (donor basin) had a minimal role in the NCT 1 project and considered it a national project. Like in other countries, IBWTs are greatly pushed by a coalition of engineers, politicians, and financiers for the most economically and politically strategic recipient regions [9, 24]. As noted in [25], since water allocation in IBWTs is largely determined by economic consideration and political will, interests for the ecosystem and less powerful communities are rarely considered. Public participation is a prerequisite for big

projects such as NCT 1 in the Kenyan constitution, however, the mechanism of the process is not adequately provided. Effective public participation depends on the legal framework that provides clear guidelines on the process, political goodwill, and social awareness, i.e. community initiatives for water issues in the region [26]. In the NCT 1 project, although there was good political will, the process lacked clear guidelines and the WRUAs were in their infancy, as they were formed in 2015.

Like many other IBWT systems, residents of Murang'a County were concerned about the drying of their rivers, over-abstractions, and future water needs [14]. Although NCT 1 was designed to abstract only flood flows, there were some doubts because flood flows occur only a few times in a year or none, especially during dry years. In [27-31], it was found that most IBWTs are sensitive to climate variability, especially during dry periods when water demand in both basins is high and supply is low. In addition, IBWTs are based on current and future water balances between the two basins (donor and recipient) however, the future is muddled in uncertainties [32]. Although there was a need to conserve the water towers and river flows, the promoters of the project did not plan to fund conservation activities. Most of the conservation works were carried out by the CFA, WRUAs, and KFS through NGO funding and WSTF. Nairobi city residents have direct benefits from water transfer however, they do not bear the total costs of water resource regeneration. This is because some proportion of the water price (opportunity cost and externalities) should be paid to the donor basin. Therefore, the recipient basin may be paying only the supply cost and not the full cost of the project, denying the donor basin the full value (sustainable) of the water resources. For economic sustainability, all the societal costs and benefits of a project must be explicitly made public and accounted for. One way is to shorten the scale of development so that solutions are localized to improve the efficiency of projects [33]. Another way is by compensating people who bear the risks of present and future losses by creating a water transfer fund from water taxes [34-35]. For instance, in NCT 1, a water fund from the water diversion could be used for conservation activities of Aberdares Forest and other externalities in Murang'a County, the donor basin. Payment of ecosystem services is more elaborated in the tourism sector in Kenya, as in the case of Narok County, where the county receives approximately 70% of its revenue from the Maasai Mara National Reserve.

V. CONCLUSION

This study presented a comprehensive stakeholder analysis of the NCT 1 water transfer project in the Upper Tana basin, Kenya. Literature review, semi-structured interviews, and FGD were used to identify and categorize stakeholders. Additionally, QCA was used to analyze the perceived benefits and risks of the project by stakeholders. A total of 25 stakeholders were identified, where AWWDA and MoWI were the promoters of the project with the highest power and influence in the decision-making process. Although WSPs and WRUAs had a high interest in the project, their participation was limited. There is an initial written consensus and agreement between the Murang'a County government and AWWDA however, the

county had limited engagement in the project implementation which impacted the agreed interventions.

The risks of the project were reduced river flows, spring drying, and generally the ability of Murang'a County residents to access water in the present and future. Benefits from the project were water supply to Nairobi city residents, employment opportunities for Murang'a County residents during the construction of the IBWT infrastructure, and a nominal water levy to the donor basin (Upper Tana). In addition to being a low annual permit fee, the water levy does not take into account the opportunity and externalities (socioeconomic/environmental costs) of the water transfers, thus not offering full/sustainable water value to the donor basin. The low water abstraction costs could be among the reasons for the high non-revenue water consumption by users in Nairobi City (recipient basin). The project did not have any conservation plan or a respective budget, therefore most of the activities were carried out by WRUAs, KFS, and CFA through local and international grants. Most stakeholders expressed the need for improved cooperation in Aberdares Forest conservation measures, as this would be beneficial for both the recipient and the donor basins. The findings suggest that most of the risks were borne in the donor basin, while the benefits were in the recipient. To balance the distribution of benefits and risks, an improved water levy to cover environmental externalities and catchment conservation would ensure sustainable value and use of water resources in both recipient and donor basins.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Z. Bischoff-Mattson, G. Maree, C. Vogel, A. Lynch, D. Olivier, and D. Terblanche, "Shape of a water crisis: practitioner perspectives on urban water scarcity and 'Day Zero' in South Africa," *Water Policy*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 193–210, Mar. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.2166/wp.2020.233>.
- [2] J. Gupta and P. van der Zaag, "Interbasin water transfers and integrated water resources management: Where engineering, science and politics interlock," *Physics and Chemistry of the Earth, Parts A/B/C*, vol. 33, no. 1, pp. 28–40, Jan. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pce.2007.04.003>.
- [3] R. C. D. Carvalho and A. Magrini, "Conflicts over Water Resource Management in Brazil: A Case Study of Inter-Basin Transfers," *Water Resources Management*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 193–213, Apr. 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11269-006-7377-3>.
- [4] G. V. Dyrnes and A. Vatn, "Who owns the water? A study of a water conflict in the Valley of Ixtlahuaca, Mexico," *Water Policy*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 295–312, Jun. 2005, <https://doi.org/10.2166/wp.2005.0019>.
- [5] A. Gohari, S. Eslamian, A. Mirchi, J. Abedi-Koupaei, A. Massah Bavani, and K. Madani, "Water transfer as a solution to water shortage: A fix that can Backfire," *Journal of Hydrology*, vol. 491, pp. 23–39, May 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2013.03.021>.
- [6] P. Roman, "The São Francisco interbasin water transfer in Brazil: tribulations of a megaproject through constraints and controversy.," *Water Alternatives*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 395–419, 2017.
- [7] World Commission on Dams, *Dams and Development: A New Framework for Decision-Making*. London, UK: Earthscan Publications Ltd, 2000.

- [8] "Feasibility Study and Master Plan For Developing New Water Sources For Nairobi and Satellite Towns: Northern Collector Tunnar Project Phase I," Ministry Of Water and Irrigation, Nairobi, Kenya, 2011.
- [9] N. Hernández-Mora, L. del Moral Ituarte, F. La-Roca, A. La Calle, and G. Schmidt, "Interbasin Water Transfers in Spain: Interregional Conflicts and Governance Responses," in *Globalized Water: A Question of Governance*, G. Schneier-Madanés, Ed. Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands, 2014, pp. 175–194.
- [10] W. Zhuang, "Eco-environmental impact of inter-basin water transfer projects: a review," *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, vol. 23, no. 13, pp. 12867–12879, Jul. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-016-6854-3>.
- [11] Y. Quan, C. Wang, Y. Yan, G. Wu, and H. Zhang, "Impact of Inter-Basin Water Transfer Projects on Regional Ecological Security from a Telecoupling Perspective," *Sustainability*, vol. 8, no. 2, Feb. 2016, Art. no. 162, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su8020162>.
- [12] M. Sadegh, N. Mahjouri, and R. Kerachian, "Optimal Inter-Basin Water Allocation Using Crisp and Fuzzy Shapley Games," *Water Resources Management*, vol. 24, no. 10, pp. 2291–2310, Aug. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11269-009-9552-9>.
- [13] J. Tian, D. Liu, S. Guo, Z. Pan, and X. Hong, "Impacts of Inter-Basin Water Transfer Projects on Optimal Water Resources Allocation in the Hanjiang River Basin, China," *Sustainability*, vol. 11, no. 7, Jan. 2019, Art. no. 2044, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11072044>.
- [14] H. Yang and A. J. B. Zehnder, "The South-North Water Transfer Project in China," *Water International*, vol. 30, no. 3, pp. 339–349, Sep. 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1080/02508060508691874>.
- [15] "Report of the Technical Committee on Northern Collector Tunnel Project," Murang'a County Government, Murang'a, Kenya, Apr. 2015.
- [16] R. J. Yang, "An investigation of stakeholder analysis in urban development projects: Empirical or rationalistic perspectives," *International Journal of Project Management*, vol. 32, no. 5, pp. 838–849, Jul. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijproman.2013.10.011>.
- [17] M. S. Reed *et al.*, "Who's in and why? A typology of stakeholder analysis methods for natural resource management," *Journal of Environmental Management*, vol. 90, no. 5, pp. 1933–1949, Apr. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2009.01.001>.
- [18] P. Enevoldsen, B. K. Sovacool, and T. Tambo, "Collaborate, involve, or defend? A critical stakeholder assessment and strategy for the Danish hydrogen electrolysis industry," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 39, no. 36, pp. 20879–20887, Dec. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2014.10.035>.
- [19] M. Mohamadian, T. Nasiri, M. Bahadori, and H. Jalilian, "Stakeholders analysis of COVID-19 management and control: a case of Iran," *BMC Public Health*, vol. 22, no. 1, Art. no. 1909, Oct. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-022-14219-0>.
- [20] D. Schlund, S. Schulte, and T. Sprenger, "The who's who of a hydrogen market ramp-up: A stakeholder analysis for Germany," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 154, Feb. 2022, Art. no. 111810, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.111810>.
- [21] E. Yeleliere, A. B. Nyamekye, P. Antwi-Agyei, and E. F. Boamah, "Strengthening climate adaptation in the northern region of Ghana: insights from a stakeholder analysis," *Climate Policy*, vol. 22, no. 9–10, pp. 1169–1185, Nov. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2022.2134085>.
- [22] F. Kaefer, J. Roper, and P. N. Sinha, "A software-assisted qualitative content analysis of news articles: Examples and reflections," *Forum: Qualitative Social Research*, vol. 16, no. 2, May 2015.
- [23] P. Mayring, "Qualitative Content Analysis," *Forum: Qualitative Social Research*, vol. 1, no. 2, Jun. 2000, <https://doi.org/10.17169/fqs-1.2.1089>.
- [24] J. D. Rinaudo and B. Barraqué, "Inter-Basin Transfers as a Supply Option: The End of an Era?," in *Understanding and Managing Urban Water in Transition*, Q. Grafton, K. A. Daniell, C. Nauges, J.-D. Rinaudo, and N. W. W. Chan, Eds. Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands, 2015, pp. 175–200.
- [25] W. Ben Fraj, M. Elloumi, and F. Molle, "The politics of interbasin transfers: socio-environmental impacts and actor strategies in Tunisia," *Natural Resources Forum*, vol. 43, no. 1, pp. 17–30, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1111/1477-8947.12165>.
- [26] A. Ballester and K. E. Mott Lacroix, "Public Participation in Water Planning in the Ebro River Basin (Spain) and Tucson Basin (U.S., Arizona): Impact on Water Policy and Adaptive Capacity Building," *Water*, vol. 8, no. 7, Jul. 2016, Art. no. 273, <https://doi.org/10.3390/w8070273>.
- [27] A. N. Laghari, W. Rauch, and M. A. Soomro, "A Hydrological Response Analysis Considering Climatic Variability: Case Study of Hunza Catchment," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 2981–2984, Jun. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2056>.
- [28] P. Sinha, E. Rollason, L. J. Bracken, J. Wainwright, and S. M. Reaney, "A new framework for integrated, holistic, and transparent evaluation of inter-basin water transfer schemes," *Science of The Total Environment*, vol. 721, Jun. 2020, Art. no. 137646, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.137646>.
- [29] S. I. Khan *et al.*, "Satellite Remote Sensing and Hydrologic Modeling for Flood Inundation Mapping in Lake Victoria Basin: Implications for Hydrologic Prediction in Ungauged Basins," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 49, no. 1, pp. 85–95, Jan. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TGRS.2010.2057513>.
- [30] N. Kumar and R. Jha, "Morphometric Analysis of Kosi River Basin, Bihar, India Using Remote Sensing and GIS Techniques," in *Climate Change Impacts on Water Resources: Hydraulics, Water Resources and Coastal Engineering*, R. Jha, V. P. Singh, V. Singh, L. B. Roy, and R. Thendiyath, Eds. Cham, Switzerland: Springer International Publishing, 2021, pp. 469–481.
- [31] N. Kumar and R. Jha, "GIS-based Flood Risk Mapping: The Case Study of Kosi River Basin, Bihar, India," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 9830–9836, Feb. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5377>.
- [32] M. N. Sharabian, S. Ahmad, and M. Karakouzian, "Climate Change and Eutrophication: A Short Review," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 3668–3672, Dec. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2392>.
- [33] H. H. G. Savenije and P. Van der Zaag, "Integrated water resources management: Concepts and issues," *Physics and Chemistry of the Earth, Parts A/B/C*, vol. 33, no. 5, pp. 290–297, Jan. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pce.2008.02.003>.
- [34] V. Yevjevich, "Water Diversions and Interbasin Transfers," *Water International*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 342–348, Sep. 2001, <https://doi.org/10.1080/02508060108686926>.
- [35] M. Mousavi, I. Ghazi, and B. Omaræe, "Risk Assessment in the Maritime Industry," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1377–1381, Feb. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.836>.

The Experimental and Theoretical Effect of Fire on the Structural Behavior of Laced Reinforced Concrete Deep Beams

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ABSTRACT

A Laced Reinforced Concrete (LRC) structural element comprises continuously inclined shear reinforcement in the form of lacing that connects the longitudinal reinforcements on both faces of the structural element. This study conducted a theoretical investigation of LRC deep beams to predict their behavior after exposure to fire and high temperatures. Four simply supported reinforced concrete beams of 1500 mm, 200 mm, and 240 mm length, width, and depth, respectively, were considered. The specimens were identical in terms of compressive strength ($f'_c \approx 40$ MPa) and steel reinforcement details. The same laced steel reinforcement ratio of 0.0035 was used. Three specimens were burned at variable durations and steady-state temperatures (one hour at 500 °C and 600 °C, and two hours at 500 °C). The flexural behavior of the simply supported deep beams, subjected to the two concentric loads in the middle third of the beam, was investigated with ABAQUS software. The results showed that the laced reinforcement with an inclination of 45° improved the structural behavior of the deep beams, and the lacing resisted failure and extended the life of the model. The optimal structural response was observed for the specimens. The laced reinforcement improved the failure mode and converted it from shear to flexure-shear failure. The parametric study showed that the lacing bars remarkably improved the strength of the deep beams and they were not affected more by the steady-state temperature and duration. Furthermore, a greater increase in load-carrying capacity was associated with an increase in the flexural diameter of approximately 12 and 16 mm by approximately 24.77% and 87.61%, respectively, compared to the reference LRC deep beams.

Keywords-laced reinforcement concrete; finite element method; self-compacting concrete; fire; high temperature; deep beam

I. INTRODUCTION

A Laced Reinforced Concrete (LRC) structure is a structural element that includes lacings and equal reinforcement on both the tension and compression faces. Due to the impact of the lacing reinforcement's truss action, the major flexural reinforcement bars are bound together on the element's face and the concrete components [1-2]. For concrete members, laced reinforcement increases ductility and improves confinement [3-5], providing greater shear resistance than traditional shear reinforcement (stirrups), which is significantly required in fortified structures [6]. In [7], it was shown that replacing the stirrups with lacings inclined at angles greater than 30° can convert the failure mode to pure flexural. In [8], the residual flexural strength of a slab was shown to be 81.5, 75, and 62.3% for fire temperatures of 300, 500, and 700 °C, respectively. Increasing compressive strength was found to

decrease the percentage of remaining flexural strength, and rapid cooling had a greater impact on the residual flexural strength than slow cooling [9]. In [10], a specimen with a 0.0065 laced steel ratio increased its ultimate load by approximately 57% compared to one without a laced ratio. In [11], a laced reinforcement slab was compared with one without laced reinforcement, showing increase in cracking load and ultimate load of approximately 28, 45, 16, and 40%, respectively. Lacing bars were proposed as a low-cost alternative to traditional stirrups to improve the overall structural response of Self-Compacting Concrete (SCC) beams [12]. Deep beams are two-dimensional elements with a high depth to length ratio. The cross-sections exhibit nonlinear deformations under bending, resulting in a nonlinear distribution of the strains across them. Exposure to elevated temperatures, mainly caused by accidental fires, represents one

of the most severe exposure conditions for buildings and structures [13-14]. This study aimed to determine the efficiency of lacing reinforcement in post-fire deep beams and the contribution of the tension reinforcement to the performance of the lacing after exposure to fire.

II. DESCRIPTION OF THE TEST SPECIMENS

This study considered 4 simply supported specimens. All specimens were identical in terms of geometrical layout with a width of 200 mm, a depth of 240 mm, and an overall length of 1500 mm. The reinforcement details of 10 mm diameter for longitudinal tension reinforcement and laced reinforcement of 8 mm in diameter with an inclination of 45° as a shear reinforcement were according to ACI-318 and UFC 3-340-02 [15-16]. The test parameters were the steady-state temperature and the duration of the fire. Three specimens were tested under the effect of a static load (two-point load) after being exposed to a fire-flame effect of different steady-state temperatures (500 and 600°C) and duration of 1 and 2 hr, while the fourth was used as a reference specimen not affected by the fire-flame effect. Figure 1 shows the dimensions and details of the beam, and Table I shows the characteristics of the tested specimens.

Fig. 1. Dimensions and details of the beam.

TABLE I. CHARACTERISTICS OF THE TESTED SPECIMENS

No.	Beam designation	Flexural diameter (mm)	Laced steel ratio	Steady-state temperature (°C)	Burning duration (h)
1	NF-REF	10	0.0035	No fire effect	-
2	F-500-1hr	10	0.0035	500	1
3	F-500-2hr	10	0.0035	500	2
4	F-600-1hr	10	0.0035	600	1

III. PROPERTIES OF THE HARDENED CONCRETE

The concrete mixtures were produced according to [17]. For the theoretical operation, hardened reinforced concrete in cubes and cylinders was tested using a specific concrete mix with specific proportions. The trial mix was cured at an average temperature of 28°C and a relative humidity of 60%. Table II shows the compressive strength (f_{cu}), splitting tensile strength (f_t), and modulus of elasticity (E_c) of the SCC to demonstrate the effect of exposure to fire on the mechanical properties of hardened concrete.

TABLE II. HARDENED PROPERTIES OF SCC

Steady-state temperature (°C)	Compressive strength (f_{cu}) (MPa)	Splitting tensile strength (f_t) (MPa)	Modulus of elasticity (E_c) (MPa)
25	57	4.01	31050
Duration (1hr)			
400	38	2.5	17100
500	35	2.33	16000
600	33	1.88	15000
700	20	1.33	12000
Duration (2 hr)			
500	32	1.91	13000
600	19	1.36	10000

IV. FINITE ELEMENT MODEL OF LRC DEEP BEAMS

To validate the experimental work, a 3D Finite Element Model (FEM) of the LRC deep beam specimen was carried out using ABAQUS to predict the flexural behavior. SCC was simulated in FEM using the Concrete Damage Plasticity Model (CDPM). All the material behaviors needed for the simulation were introduced directly into the selected models using the stress-strain behavior from the experimental investigation. A 3D 8-noded linear brick element (C3D8R: 8-node linear hexahedral reduced integration hourglass control) was used to model the concrete beam and the supporting plate, while a 2-noded element (T3D2: 2-noded linear 3D truss element type) was used for the lacing steel bar, longitudinal steel bar, and stirrups. Figure 2 shows the discretized beam elements and the assembly of concrete and steel bars. Embedded region limitations were used to combine two surfaces during a simulation for the burned and reference beams, where every node on the surface was compelled to have the same motion as the closest point on the master surface with a frictionless contact property. Figure 3 shows the formulation of connecting interaction states in the model.

Fig. 2. Finite element model of the RC Beam in ABAQUS.

Fig. 3. Formulation of connected interaction-states in the model.

CDPM was used to simulate the nonlinear behavior of SCC [18-19]. This model requires the values of the modulus of elasticity and Poisson's ratio, and the description of compressive and tensile stress-plastic strain behavior, which were investigated experimentally and are shown in Table II. Table III shows the plastic damage parameters needed for the CDPM simulation in ABAQUS. The compressive stress-strain response of the SCC is necessary to analyze and design SCC members [20].

A. Concrete's Thermal Characteristics

Thermal conductivity defines a material's capacity to conduct heat by the ratio of heat flux and temperature gradient. It depicts the uniform flow of heat through the concrete of a thickness unit over a unit area subjected to a unit temperature difference between the two opposing faces. The conductivity of concrete is defined as a function of temperature [21]:

$$\lambda_c \left(\frac{W}{mK} \right) = 2 - \frac{0.24T}{120} + 0.012 \left(\frac{T}{120} \right)^2, \quad 20 \leq T \leq 1200^\circ C \quad (1)$$

where λ_c is the thermal conductivity and T is the temperature.

Specific heat refers to the quantity of heat per mass unit required to elevate a substance's temperature by one degree. Specific heat is a function of temperature given by [21]:

$$C_c \left(\frac{J}{kgK} \right) = 900 + \frac{80T}{120} - 4 \left(\frac{T}{120} \right)^2, \quad 20 \leq T \leq 1200^\circ C \quad (2)$$

where C_c is the specific heat and T is the temperature.

When exposed to a temperature change, concrete's isotropic nature causes it to exhibit thermal expansion. Stresses that result from non-uniform thermal expansion in concrete structures cause cracking. Eurocode 2 defines the thermal expansion of concrete as:

$$\epsilon_{th}(T) = \begin{cases} -1.8 \times 10^{-4} + 9 \times 10^{-6}T + 2.3 \times 10^{-11}T^3, & 20^\circ C \leq T \leq 700^\circ C \\ 14 \times 10^{-3}, & 700^\circ C \leq T \leq 1200^\circ C \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where ϵ_{th} is the thermal expansion and T is the temperature.

TABLE III. CONCRETE DAMAGE PLASTICITY PARAMETERS

Parameter	Selected value
Material model	CDP model
Dilation angle	45
ϵ	0.1
Fb/ft_0	1.16
K	0.667
Viscosity parameter	0.0001

B. Steel's Thermal Properties

Steel has a variety of mechanical characteristics, including mass density, Young's modulus, and Poisson's ratio. Steel maintains its mass density (7850 kg/m³) even at high temperatures. Temperature impacts steel's Young modulus. The values for the steel modulus of elasticity (E_s) at high temperatures are prescribed by Eurocode 3 [22]. On the other hand, Poisson's ratio is considered to be constant (0.3) at all temperatures [23]. The uniaxial stress-strain relationship for steel in the FEMs was idealized as a bilinear curve and was expected to behave as an elastic-plastic model with strain hardening. Thermal conductivity (λ_c), specific heat (C_s), and

thermal expansion (ϵ_{th}) are all thermal properties of steel. The following formulae are used by Eurocode 3 to define these attributes as functions of temperature:

$$\lambda_c \left(\frac{W}{mK} \right) = \begin{cases} 54 - 3.33 \times 10^{-2}T, & 20 \leq T < 800^\circ C \\ 27.3, & 800 < T < 1200^\circ C \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$C_s (J/kgK) = \begin{cases} 425 + 7.73 \times 10^{-1}T - 1.69 \times 10^{-3}T^2 + 7.73 \times 10^{-6}T^3, & 20 \leq T < 600^\circ C \\ 666 + \frac{13003}{738-T}, & 600 < T \leq 735^\circ C \\ 545 + \frac{17820}{T-731}, & 735 < T \leq 900^\circ C \\ 650, & 900 < T \leq 1200^\circ C \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

$$\epsilon_{th}(T) = \begin{cases} -2.416 \times 10^{-4} + 1.5 \times 10^{-5}T + 0.4 \times 10^{-8}T^2, & 20 \leq T < 750^\circ C \\ 1.1 \times 10^{-2}, & 750 < T \leq 860^\circ C \\ -6.2 \times 10^{-4} + 2 \times 10^{-5}T, & 860 < T \leq 1200^\circ C \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. FEA Observations

The crack patterns observed in the FEMs showed a combined flexure-shear failure, as the lacing reinforcement improves the behavior of the specimens and converts the failure mode from shear to flexure-shear failure. The first flexural crack was observed on the tension surface directly below the loading points, where the bending moment was the largest. Thereafter, inclined cracks appeared in the shear span when increasing the applied load. As the load increased, both crack types grew, enlarged, and propagated upward, causing the failure of these beams, followed by the crushing of the concrete. For an even comparison of responses of different specimens in finite element analysis, all FEMs were compared at the ultimate load. The damage region for tension and compression is described by concrete compression damage (dc) and concrete tension damage (dt), according to the ABAQUS software documentation. Figure 4 shows the finite element analysis observations for crack patterns.

Fig. 4. Tension cracks pattern for specimens.

B. Load-Displacement Behavior

In terms of the effect of the burning duration, Figure 5 shows the load-displacement curves for the burning specimens,

indicating a decrease in load-carrying capacity with increasing fire duration compared to the reference beam. The decrease was approximately 18.58 and 26.55% with increasing fire duration from 1 to 2 hr at 500 °C, respectively. Figure 5 also shows that an increase in steady-state temperature resulted in a decrease in load-carrying capacity compared to the reference beam. The decrease was approximately 18.58 and 30.08% with increasing steady-state temperature from 500 to 600 °C, respectively, at 1 hr of burn duration.

Fig. 5. Load-displacement behavior.

The vertical deflection at mid-span was measured for the ultimate load for all specimens. Compared to the reference specimen, a decrease in deflection was observed at the ultimate load, of approximately 19.87, 25.69, and 33.85%, with increasing steady-state temperature and duration. Table IV shows the variation of the ultimate load and deflection. The effect of lacing reinforcement was clear, when the beam failed, it got up again and showed resistance, improving the specimen's strength and leading to an increase in load-carrying capacity and displacement.

TABLE IV. ULTIMATE LOAD AND DEFLECTION.

Specimens	P_u (kN)	Variation %	Δu (mm)	Variation %
NF-REF	113	-	37.64	-
F-500-1hr	92	-18.58	30.16	-19.87
F-500-2hr	83	-26.55	27.97	-25.69
F-600-1hr	79	-30.08	24.90	-33.85

In terms of the energy absorbed by the LRC deep beams exposed to fire, the burning reduced the toughness of the specimens. The absorbed energy at the ultimate load was 3685.44, 2425.68, 1805.70, and 1572.85 kNmm for the specimens NF-REF, F-500-1hr, F-500-2hr, and F-600-1hr, respectively, as shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 6. Absorption energy index for laced reinforcement specimens.

VI. PARAMETRIC STUDY

Two diameters of flexural bars, 12 and 16 mm, were selected to investigate the effect of the area of the flexural bars on the structural behavior of the concrete deep beams. The other properties were kept constant and the adopted lacing angle was 45°. Figure 7 shows the load-deflection responses of the two beams, indicating a larger increase in load-carrying capacity with an increase in the flexural diameter from 10 to 12 and 16 mm, by approximately 24.77 and 87.61%, respectively. The tension and lacing strain values at the flexural span achieved a 0.003 micro-strain, which is presented in Figure 8.

Fig. 7. Influence of the flexural bar diameter.

Fig. 8. Load-steel strains with different diameters of flexural rebar.

To investigate the influence of various steady-state temperatures and durations on the behavior of LRC deep beams for SCC, burning of 400 and 700 °C for 1hr and 600 °C for 2 hr were numerically investigated while keeping the other properties constant. The results confirmed that the laced bars remarkably improved the strength of the deep beams and were not affected more by the steady-state temperature and duration. A decrease in the load-carrying capacity was observed with increasing steady-state temperature and duration compared to the reference beam. On the other hand, Figure 9 shows the displacement at the failure load with increasing steady-state temperature and duration of the fire. Figure 10 shows the strains in lacings and tension flexural reinforcement located at

the shear span of the beams with different steady-state temperatures at various durations.

Fig. 9. Load displacement behavior for changing steady-state temperature.

Fig. 10. Load-steel strains with changing temperature.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, laced reinforcement with an inclination of 45° in deep beams after exposure to fire flame was numerically investigated. The following conclusions were derived:

- Laced reinforcement improved the structural behavior of the deep beams. The behavior of beams was found to be significantly affected by the lacing. The lacing resists failure and extends model life. Optimal structural response was observed for burned specimens compared to the reference beam.
- The laced reinforcement converts the failure mode of a deep beam from shear to combined flexure-shear failure.
- The laced reinforcement increased flexural toughness at the failure load for the burned specimens by increasing the resistance of the beam, which improved the load-displacement behavior.
- The finite element analysis observations of the parametric study showed that the lacing bars remarkably improved the

strength of the deep beams and were not affected more by the steady-state temperature and duration when they were increased to 700°C and 2 hr, respectively.

REFERENCES

- [1] N. Sudharsan, C. J. B. Grant, P. Murthi, K. Poongodi, and P. M. Kumar, "A Comparative Experimental Investigation on Laced Reinforced Concrete Beam and Conventional Beam under Monotonic Loading," *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, vol. 822, no. 1, Apr. 2021, Art. no. 012034, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/822/1/012034>.
- [2] S. Narayanasamy and B. Grant, "Structural Behaviour of Laced Reinforced Concrete Elements - A survey," *International Journal of Current Engineering and Scientific Research*, vol. 4, no. 12, pp. 36–41, Jan. 2017.
- [3] N. Anandavalli, N. Lakshmanan, A. Prakash, J. Rajasankar, and N. R. Iyer, "Numerical Investigations on a Blast Loaded Laced Reinforced Concrete Structure using an Equivalent Constitutive Property," *Journal of The Institution of Engineers (India): Series A*, vol. 96, no. 4, pp. 311–318, Dec. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40030-015-0139-6>.
- [4] A. I. Abdullah and S. D. M. Al-Khazraji, "Structural Behavior of High Strength Laced Reinforced Concrete One Way Slab Exposed to Fire Flame," *Civil Engineering Journal*, vol. 5, no. 12, pp. 2747–2761, Dec. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.28991/cej-2019-03091446>.
- [5] N. Anandavalli *et al.*, "Behaviour of a Blast Loaded Laced Reinforced Concrete Structure," *Defence Science Journal*, vol. 62, no. 5, pp. 284–289, Sep. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.14429/dsj.62.820>.
- [6] G. M. Colyvas, Y. Malecot, Y. Sieffert, S. Aboudha, and C. Kanali, "Behavior of Reinforced Concrete Beams using Wire Rope as Internal Shear Reinforcement," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 5940–5946, Aug. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3496>.
- [7] T. S. Al-Gasham, J. M. Mhalhal, and S. R. Abid, "Flexural Behavior of Laced Reinforced Concrete Moderately Deep Beams," *Case Studies in Construction Materials*, vol. 13, Dec. 2020, Art. no. e00363, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cscm.2020.e00363>.
- [8] A. A. Hammadi, A. F. Izzat, and J. A. Farhan, "Effect of Fire Flame (High Temperature) on the Self Compacted Concrete (SCC) One Way Slabs," *Journal of Engineering*, vol. 18, no. 10, pp. 1083–1099, Jul. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.31026/j.eng.2012.10.01>.
- [9] S. D. Mohammed and N. M. Fawzi, "Fire Flame Influence on the Behavior of reinforced Concrete Beams Affected by Repeated Load," *Journal of Engineering*, vol. 22, no. 9, pp. 206–223, Sep. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.31026/j.eng.2016.09.13>.
- [10] H. A. Jabir, "The behavior of one-way concrete slab with lacing reinforcement subjected to static and repeated load," Ph.D. dissertation, University of Baghdad, Iraq, 2016.
- [11] A. F. Hallawi and A. H. A. Al-Ahmed, "Enhancing the Behavior of One-Way Reinforced Concrete Slabs by Using Laced Reinforcement," *Civil Engineering Journal*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 718–728, Mar. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.28991/cej-2019-03091282>.
- [12] T. Ofuyatan, F. A. Olutoge, and A. Olowofoyeku, "Durability Properties of Palm Oil Fuel Ash Self Compacting Concrete," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 753–756, Feb. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.524>.
- [13] N. F. Hussen and S. D. Mohammed, "Influence of Fire-Flame Duration and Temperature on the Behavior of Reinforced Concrete Beam Containing Water Absorption Polymer Sphere; Numerical Investigation," *Journal of Engineering*, vol. 28, no. 11, pp. 67–84, Nov. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.31026/j.eng.2022.11.06>.
- [14] M. Baghdadi, M. S. Dimia, and D. Baghdadi, "A Parametric Study of Fire-Damaged Reinforced Concrete Columns under Lateral Loads," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 9113–9119, Oct. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5172>.
- [15] J. P. Moehle, "Key Changes in the 2019 Edition of the ACI Building Code (ACI 318-19)," *Concrete International*, vol. 41, no. 8, pp. 21–27, Aug. 2019.

-
- [16] "Guidelines for Self-Compacting Concrete," European Federation for Specialist Construction Chemicals and Concrete Systems, Norfolk, UK, 2002.
- [17] "The European Guidelines for Self-Compacting Concrete," European Federation for Specialist Construction Chemicals and Concrete Systems, Norfolk, UK, 2005.
- [18] M. Neuenschwander, M. Knobloch, and M. Fontana, "Suitability of the damage-plasticity modelling concept for concrete at elevated temperatures: Experimental validation with uniaxial cyclic compression tests," *Cement and Concrete Research*, vol. 79, pp. 57–75, Jan. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconres.2015.07.013>.
- [19] L. T. Yaw, J. B. Osei, and M. Adom-Asamoah, "On The Non-Linear Finite Element Modelling of Self-Compacting Concrete Beams," *Journal of Structural Transportation Studies*, vol. 2, no. 2, 2017.
- [20] J. Lubliner, J. Oliver, S. Oller, and E. Oñate, "A plastic-damage model for concrete," *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, vol. 25, no. 3, pp. 299–326, Jan. 1989, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0020-7683\(89\)90050-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0020-7683(89)90050-4).
- [21] "Eurocode 2: Design of concrete structures," European Committee for Standardization, Brussels, Belgium, European Standard EN 1992-1-2, 2004.
- [22] A. Nussbaumer, L. Borges, and L. Davaine, *Fatigue Design of Steel and Composite Structures: Eurocode 3: Design of Steel Structures, Part 1-9 Fatigue; Eurocode 4: Design of Composite Steel and Concrete Structures*. Berlin, Germany: European Convention for Constructional Steelwork, 2011.
- [23] S. J. George and Y. Tian, "Structural Performance of Reinforced Concrete Flat Plate Buildings Subjected to Fire," *International Journal of Concrete Structures and Materials*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 111–121, Jun. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40069-012-0011-2>.

A Study on the Evaluation of the Compression Behavior of PLA Lattice Structures Manufactured by FDM

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ABSTRACT

The paper brings forward the results of a study on the compression test of 28 lattice structures made of PLA by FDM, with the height of the deposited layer at a pass of $H_s = 0.20$ mm and 50% filling percentage P_u . The 28 samples were made on Anycubic 4 Max Pro 2.0 the 3D printer, considering 7 filling patterns: Grid, Tri-hexagon, Octet, Triangles, Cubic subdivision, Gyroid, and Cross 3D for each type of lattice structure. The dimensions of the specimens, before and after the compression test, were determined using the DeMeet 3D coordinate measuring machine. In this context, a minimum printing accuracy value of 98.98% and a maximum deformation value of 57.70% were recorded for the lattice structure corresponding to the Triangles fill pattern. For the same Triangles type lattice structure, the highest average maximum compressive force of 87.32 kN was obtained. The maximization of the ratio between the use value and the production cost, one of the fundamental technical-economic principles of value analysis, was obtained for the lattice structure corresponding to the Cubic subdivision filling model.

Keywords -FDM; PLA; lattice structure; infill pattern; slicer; compression; experimental tests; value analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

In the last 30 years, additive manufacturing technologies have continuously evolved and have been embraced by numerous industries [1-2]. The interest was sparked by the advantages they have in comparison to the conventional formative and subtractive technologies [13-17]. The main advantages of additive manufacturing technologies are: low manufacturing costs, short time for landmark making, control over the way the parts are made (adjustment of process parameters), making complex geometries without designing the base and fixing landmark, and the amount of technological waste is insignificant [4]. The optimization of printing parameters is an important criterion as they have a direct impact on the mechanical characteristics of the produced landmark.

Authors in [5] presented the results of the compression test of some Ti6Al4V lattice structures, manufactured by SLM additive technology. In [6], the influence of the filling pattern

on the mechanical characteristics of the samples manufactured by DLP additive technology was studied, the best results being obtained for the Gyroid filling pattern. In [7], the influence of the variable parameters, H_s - the height of the layer deposited in one pass and P_u - the filling percentage, on the compression behavior of the samples manufactured by FDM additive technology, from PLA, ABS and thermally treated PLA, was studied. The authors' conclusion is that with a decrease in the height of the layer deposited at a pass (H_s), an increase in the compression stress is recorded.

In this context, the compression behavior of 21 lattice structures (specimens) manufactured of PLA by FDM will be evaluated, using the constant parameters from Table I, with 3 pieces for each of the 7 filling models: Grid, Tri-hexagon, Octet, Triangles, Cubic subdivision, Gyroid, Cross 3D. The accuracy of FDM printing and the maximum compressive strain value of the lattice structures, before and after the compression test, will be determined by measuring them in the Z plane. Using the experimental data and the fundamental

principle of value analysis to maximize the ratio of utility value and the production cost [8-11] of all the analyzed filling patterns, we will establish the optimal option from a technical and economic point of view for the manufacture of compression-resistant lattice structures from PLA by FDM.

II. DESIGN, FABRICATION, MEASUREMENT, AND COMPRESSION TESTING OF LATTICE STRUCTURES

The 3D model of the specimen (lattice structure) was designed in SolidWorks 2023 [19] and has the dimensions shown in Figure 1. The 3D model of the sample was converted to *.STL format. In order to set the printing parameters presented in Table I the Cura slicer [18] was used.

Fig. 1. 3D model of the specimen for the compression test.

TABLE I. FDM PRINTING OF PLA LATTICE STRUCTURES PARAMETERS

Constant parameters	Filling pattern	Printed parts (Items)	Mass of the piece (Kg)
Piece orientation, X - Y	-	4	0.069
Extruder temperature, $T_e = 200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	Grid		0.038
	Tri-hexagon		0.069
	Octet		0.069
	Triangles		0.069
	Cubic subdivision		0.069
Table temperature, $T_b = 60\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	Gyroid		0.069
Print speed, $V_p = 40\text{ mm/s}$	Cross 3D	0.052	
Height of the deposited layer, $H_s = 0.20\text{ mm}$			
Fill percentage, $P_u = 50\%$			
Wall thickness, $W_t = 0.80\text{ mm}$			

Figure 2 shows the filling models used for the FDM fabrication of the specimens (lattice shells) from PLA. The 3D printer - Anycubic 4 Max Pro 2.0 (Figure 3) was used to make the lattice structures. It has a printing volume of 270x210x190 mm and uses additive FDM technology. The semifinished product used for FDM manufacturing of lattice structures is PLA filament with 1.75 mm diameter (Filafill). With the 3D printer in Figure 3, using the constant parameters from Table I, we made 28 lattice structures, sets of 4 for each 7 filling patterns, as shown in Figure 2. The 28 lattice structures were measured in the Z plane using the DeMeet 3D machine (Figure 5(a)). The data are centralized in Table III.

Fig. 2. Filling patterns used for the manufacture of lattice structures from PLA by FDM: (a) Grid, (b) Tri-hexagon, (c) Octet, (d) Triangles, (e) Cubic subdivision, (f) Gyroid, (g) Cross 3D.

We tested 21 of the constructed items for compression on a Microcomputer controlled electronic Universal Testing Machine (UTM) - TIME WDW-300M series 0306. The compression Tests (Figure 4) were performed according to the ISO 604:2002 standard, at a speed of 5 mm/min [20].

Fig. 3. The Anycubic 4 Max Pro 2.0 3D printer, used to manufacture the lattice structures from PLA through FDM.

Fig. 4. Compression test of the lattice structure made of PLA by FDM. 1: loading direction, 2: sample, 3: the platens of the UTM.

After the compression test, the 21 lattice structures were measured in the Z plane using the DeMeet 3D machine (Figure 5(b)). The data are shown in Table III.

Fig. 5. Determining the dimensions of the lattice structure made of PLA by FDM, with the coordinate measuring machine - DeMeet 3D: (a) before and (b) after the compression test.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Compression Testing

The results of the compression test of the 21 lattice structures are shown in Table II and are graphically represented in Figures 6-12.

TABLE II. COMPRESSION TEST RESULTS OF THE LATTICE STRUCTURES MADE OF PLA BY FDM

Filling pattern	Maximum compressive force, F _{mc} , (kN)			Average maximum compressive force, MF _{mc} , (kN)
	Sample			
	1	2	3	
Grid	87.4	86.2	86.68	86.76
Tri-hexagon	19.33	19.06	19.32	19.24
Octet	53.31	53.48	52.60	53.13
Triangles	87.62	87.02	87.32	87.32
Cubic subdivision	54.83	53.21	55.98	54.67
Gyroid	64.79	63.63	64.99	64.47
Cross 3D	23.04	20.9	19.36	21.01

Fig. 6. Compression tests graphs of the lattice structures made of PLA by FDM, Grid filling pattern.

Fig. 7. Compression tests graphs of the lattice structures made of PLA by FDM, Tri-hexagon filling pattern.

Fig. 8. Compression tests graphs of the lattice structures made of PLA by FDM, Octet filling pattern.

Fig. 9. Compression tests graphs of the lattice structures made of PLA by FDM, Triangles filling pattern.

Fig. 10. Compression tests graphs of the lattice structures made of PLA by FDM, Cubic subdivision filling pattern.

Fig. 11. Compression tests graphs of the lattice structures made of PLA by FDM, Gyroid filling pattern.

Fig. 12. Compression tests graphs of the lattice structures made of PLA by FDM, Cross 3D filling pattern.

Figure 13 shows the average values of the maximum compression forces (Table II) for the 7 filling patterns used for the fabrication of the lattice structures of PLA by FDM.

Fig. 13. Average maximum compressive forces for each filling pattern of lattice structures made of PLA by FDM.

It can be observed that the average values of the maximum compression forces for the 7 filling models fall range between 19.24 and 87.34 kN. The highest average value of the maximum compressive forces is 87.32 kN and was obtained for the Triangles lattice structure.

B. Determination of FDM 3D Printing Accuracy and Compressive Strain of the PLA Lattice Structures

All the 28 lattice structures made of PLA by FDM (Figure 2) on the Anycubic 4 Max Pro 2.0 3D printer (Figure 3) were measured in the Z plane using the DeMeet 3D machine (Figure 5(a)). Twenty one of the samples were measured in the same plane and with the same machine after being tested in compression (Figure 5(b)). The average values of the heights of the lattice structures made of PLA by FDM, calculated for each of the filling patterns of Figure 2, before and after their compression test, are shown in Table III.

TABLE III. ACCURACY OF FDM 3D PRINTING AND COMPRESSIVE DEFORMATION OF PLA LATTICE STRUCTURES

Filling pattern	The average height of lattice structure, (mm)		Printing accuracy 3D, (%)	Compression strain, (%)
	Before compression	After compression		
Grid	48.79	27.50	99.61	55.55
Tri-hexagon	48.50	27.98	99.57	56.36
Octet	48.76	27.14	99.78	54.04
Triangles	48.89	26.42	98.98	57.70
Cubic subdivision	48.83	27.14	99.41	56.76
Gyroid	48.81	27.11	99.51	55.67
Cross 3D	48.71	27.65	99.65	55.86

The values corresponding to the 3D printing accuracy for the 7 filling patterns range from 98.98 to 99.78 %, the maximum value of the accuracy being determined for the case of the Octet type filling pattern.

The values of compression range from 54.04 to 57.70 %, the maximum value of the deformation being determined for the case of the Triangles filling pattern.

At a variation between 0.11 and 1.02 % of the 3D printing accuracy, a variation of 3.66 % of the compression strain was obtained.

C. Setting the Optimal Option from a Technical and Economic Point of View for the Manufacture of Compression-resistant Lattice Structures of PLA by FDM

Using the fundamental principle of analyzing the maximization value of the ratio between the use value V_i and the production cost C_p [8-12] we identified the optimal filling pattern from the technical and economic point of view as to manufacture compression-resistant lattice structures of PLA by FDM:

$$\frac{V_i}{C_p} \rightarrow \max. \quad (1)$$

In this study, the use value depends on the lattice structure density, which is calculated by:

$$\rho = \frac{m}{v}, \quad (2)$$

where m represents the mass of the lattice structure (sample) and v is its volume.

The volume of the lattice structure (sample) with $L=49$ mm (Figure 1) is:

$$V = L^3 = 118 \times 10^{-6} \text{m}^3. \quad (3)$$

To calculate the production cost, we used the relation:

$$C_p = C_{mat} \times P_m + T_e \times C_{en} \times P_{en}, \quad (4)$$

where C_p represents the production cost, C_{mat} is the material consumption, P_m is the material price (26 euro/kg), T_e is the execution time, C_{en} is the energy consumption (0.23 kWh), and P_{en} is the electricity price (0.26 euros/kWh).

Table IV shows the results of the performed calculations using (1)-(4), for the 7 filling models used in the manufacture of lattice structures from PLA by FDM, to determine the values of the V_i/C_p ratio.

Figure 14 uses the values of the V_i/C_p ratios shown in Table IV and the 7 filling patterns used for the manufacture of the lattice structures of PLA by FDM (Figure 2).

TABLE IV. V_i/C_p RATIO DETERMINATION

Filling pattern	Density, $\rho = V_i$	Manufacturing time, T_e	Production cost, C_p	$\frac{V_i}{C_p}$
	kg/m ³			
Grid	584.75	5.40	2.12	276.22
Tri-hexagon	322.03	5.37	1.31	246.03
Octet	584.75	5.41	2.12	276.15
Triangles	584.75	5.50	2.12	275.45
Cubic subdivision	584.75	3.35	1.99	293.20
Gyroid	584.75	9.47	2.36	247.76
Cross 3D	440.68	7.33	1.79	246.12

Fig. 14. Values of the V_i/C_p ratio for each filling pattern of lattice structures made of PLA by FDM.

In Figure 14, we notice that the maximum value of the V_i/C_p ratio is 293.20 kg/(m³ × euro) and was obtained for the case of the Cubic subdivision filling pattern. This is the optimal option from the technical and economic point of view for PLA manufacturing by FDM of compression-resistant lattice structures.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

- The accuracy of FDM fabrication of PLA lattice structures on the Anycubic 4 Max Pro 2.03D printer, using the constant parameters shown in Table I for the 7 filling patterns shown in Figure 2 is very good (Table III), and ranges between 98.98 and 99.78 %, with the maximum value of the precision determined for the case of the Octet type filling pattern.
- The maximum value of compressive strain of 57.70 % was determined for the Triangles filling pattern. The values of the compression strains for the 7 filling patterns used in the FDM fabrication of the lattice structures range from 54.04 to 57.70 %.
- The maximum compression force values were obtained from the Triangles type (Figure 13). In this case, an average of the maximum compression forces of 87.32 kN was obtained (Table II). In [6], the Gyroid type was considered as the proper choice due to its good mechanical resistance. Taking in consideration the mechanical proprieties of pieces made by FDM from PLA, Gyroid it is a good solution, but we have better options like Triangles and Grid (see Table II).
- From the technical-economic point of view, the optimal solution to manufacture compression-resistant lattice structures from PLA by FDM is the Cubic subdivision type, for which the highest value of the ratio between the use value ($V_i = r$) and the production cost was obtained (C_p).

The results of the current study can be widely used in different contexts using other process parameters, other materials, and/or other types of mechanical tests.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Srivastava and S. Rathee, "Additive manufacturing: recent trends, applications and future outlooks," *Progress in Additive Manufacturing*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 261–287, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40964-021-00229-8>.
- [2] D. G. Zisopol, D. V. Iacob, and A. I. Portoaca, "A Theoretical-Experimental Study of the Influence of FDM Parameters on PLA Spur

- Gear Stiffness." *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 9329–9335, Oct. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5183>.
- [3] D. G. Zisopol, M. Minescu, and D. V. Iacob, "A Theoretical-Experimental Study on the Influence of FDM Parameters on the Dimensions of Cylindrical Spur Gears Made of PLA," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 10471–10477, Apr. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5733>.
- [4] M. Mehrpouya, A. Vosooghnia, A. Dehghanghadikolaei, and B. Fotovvati, "Chapter 2 - The benefits of additive manufacturing for sustainable design and production," in *Sustainable Manufacturing*, K. Gupta and K. Salonitis, Eds. Elsevier, 2021, pp. 29–59.
- [5] Z. Alomar and F. Concli, "Compressive behavior assessment of a newly developed circular cell-based lattice structure," *Materials & Design*, vol. 205, Jul. 2021, Art. no. 109716, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2021.109716>.
- [6] R. Sava, D. A. Apostol, and D. M. Constantinescu, "Evaluation of the mechanical behavior of 3D printed cellular metamaterials with special geometries," *Proceedings of the Romanian Academy, Series A*, vol. 24, no. 1/2023, pp. 63–72, 2023.
- [7] D. G. Zisopol, I. Nae, and A. I. Portoaca, "Compression Behavior of FFF Printed Parts Obtained by Varying Layer Height and Infill Percentage," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 9747–9751, Dec. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5488>.
- [8] D. Zisopol, "The Place and Role of Value Analysis in the Restructuring of Production (Case Study)," *Economic Insights – Trends and Challenges*, vol. I, no. 4, pp. 27–35, Jan. 2012.
- [9] D. G. Zisopol, *Ingineria valorii*. Ploiesti, Romania: Editura Universității Petrol - Gaze din Ploiești, 2004.
- [10] D. G. Zisopol and A. Dumitrescu, *Ecotehnologie: Studii de caz*. Ploiesti, Romania: Editura Universității Petrol - Gaze din Ploiești, 2020.
- [11] D. G. Zisopol, A. Dumitrescu, and C. N. Trifan *Ecotehnologie. Noțiuni teoretice, aplicații și studii de caz*. Ploiesti, Romania: Editura Universității Petrol - Gaze din Ploiești, 2010.
- [12] M. T. Fernandes, "VALUE ANALYSIS: Going into a Further Dimension," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 781–789, Apr. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.535>.
- [13] D. G. Zisopol and A. Dumitrescu, *Materiale și tehnologii primare. Aplicații practice și studii de caz*. Ploiesti, Romania: Editura Universității Petrol - Gaze din Ploiești, 2005.
- [14] D. G. Zisopol and M. J. Săvulescu, *Bazele tehnologiei*. Ploiesti, Romania: Editura Universității Petrol - Gaze din Ploiești, 2003.
- [15] M. J. Săvulescu, D. G. Zisopol, and I. Nae, *Bazele tehnologiei materialelor. Îndrumar de lucrări practice*. Ploiești, Romania: Editura Premier Ploiești, 1997.
- [16] D. G. Zisopol, *Tehnologii industriale și de construcții, Aplicații practice și studii de caz*. Ploiesti, Romania: Editura Universității Petrol - Gaze din Ploiești, 2003.
- [17] M. Minescu and D. G. Zisopol, *Sudarea țevilor și fittingurilor din polietilenă de înaltă densitate*, Ploiesti, Romania: Editura Universității Petrol - Gaze din Ploiești, 2021.
- [18] "UltiMaker Cura," *UltiMaker*. <https://ultimaker.com/software/ultimaker-cura/>.
- [19] "3D CAD Design Software," *Solidworks*. <https://www.solidworks.com/home-page-2021>.
- [20] *ISO/TC 61/SC 2 Technical Committee, ISO 604:2002. Plastics — Determination of compressive properties. ISO, 2022.*

Efficient and Secure Access Control for IoT-based Environmental Monitoring

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ABSTRACT

Environmental monitoring devices based on IoT collect a large amount of data about the environment and our surroundings. These data are collected and processed before being uploaded to third-party servers and accessed and viewed by ordinary or specialized users. However, they may hold sensitive information that should not be exposed to unauthorized users. Therefore, accessing this sensitive information must be strictly controlled and limited in order to prevent unauthorized access. This research intends to create an access control mechanism based on distributed ledger technologies. The idea is to use a hybrid of IOTA technology and Ciphertext-Policy Attribute-Based Signcryption (CP-ABSC) technology. The permissions to access these data are written in a token, and this token will be sent to the Tangle after being signcrypted with CP-ABSC. Consequently, the data will be safeguarded, their confidentiality and integrity will be maintained, and unauthorized individuals will be unable to access the information. The proposed system was evaluated in terms of performance and the results showed that the system is straightforward, rapid, and convenient to use. Furthermore, a security assessment was conducted by running several scenarios to evaluate its feasibility and protection.

Keywords-ciphertext-policy; attribute-based signcryption; IOTA; access control; Internet of things (IoT); user authentication; privacy

I. INTRODUCTION

Intelligent electronic devices are nowadays not limited to smartphones, but ubiquitous. These devices gather and analyze data in order to provide us with detailed information about our surroundings. These devices communicate via the Internet of Things (IoT), which allows information to be transferred between smart devices, analyzed, and displayed as usable information. The number of IoT applications is staggering and covers a wide range of topics, including IoT-based healthcare systems, IoT-based smart industries, IoT-based smart cities, and IoT-based environmental monitoring [1, 2], which will be the focus of the current paper. Environmental monitoring is a critical IoT application that involves monitoring the surrounding environment and reporting the results for effective short-term solutions. It plays a significant role in promoting a

safe quality of life. Nevertheless, to produce accurate data, environmental monitoring necessitates the use of specialized instruments and resources. This sort of information is critical because it assists in the early detection of any potential issues and aids workers and scientists in improving and well-managing the environment [3].

IoT devices typically acquire sensitive and confidential data that must be safeguarded. However, these devices frequently employ sensors that are susceptible to security flaws. One significant security threat is the unauthorized access to IoT data and resources, which might be exploited by a malicious user or utilized for any type of abuse [4]. Furthermore, the collected data by IoT devices are subsequently sent to a cloud or server hosted by a third party. But, since the third party is considered an untrusted entity, the gathered data may be insecure and

disclosed, allowing unauthorized parties to exploit them unlawfully. Therefore, the data must be safeguarded in numerous ways that can be taken into consideration, including restricting access or encryption. Accordingly, an advanced technology that employs Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) for IoT access control called IOTA was established to implement robust access control to the resources and data acquired by IoT devices. IOTA is an excellent alternative to blockchain since it has overcome the shortcomings of blockchain in terms of throughput and fees, whereby IOTA is a technology with high throughput and no fees, making it an ideal alternative [5]. IOTA's DLT is referred to as the Tangle. A Tangle is an IOTA network of connected nodes. Data recorded in the Tangle in the form of objects are called a "transaction", and once written in the Tangle, they cannot be deleted or modified. In this research, IOTA technology will be combined with Ciphertext-Policy Attribute-Based Signcryption (CP-ABSC) to build a secure and efficient access control that will guarantee confidentiality, authenticity, and integrity by signing and encrypting the token that will contain the access rights as well as the resources and data stored in the cloud, whereby only authorized users will be able to decode this token and get access to the resources.

II. RELATED WORK

Countless studies have been conducted in the fields of DLT and attribute-based access control. Numerous methodologies have been employed to provide solutions for secure access control while preserving data protection, including blockchain [6] and machine learning [7]. The recent research that has been conducted in areas related to IoT will be discussed in this section.

The strategy developed in [8] to cope with the massive volume of data created by IoT devices is a lightweight ABSC (LH-ABSC) technique that combines Ciphertext-Policy Attribute-Based Encryption (CP-ABE) and Key-Policy Attribute-Based Signature (KP-ABS). The authors use a fog-cloud architecture to offload most of the computational overhead, such as signature, verification, and decryption. LH-ABSC has a constant signature size and meets public verification, which is critical for IoT devices. As a result, LH-ABSC provides confidentiality, unforgeability, and verifiability, in addition to selectively chosen-ciphertext security, selectively chosen-message security, and signer anonymity.

Researchers tend to implement blockchain as one of the DLTs to take advantage of its benefits, which include decentralization, auditability, immutability, and consensus. Authors in [7] developed an Intrusion Detection System (IDS) in IoT using machine learning and Blockchain. Authors in [9] suggested an IoT device access control mechanism based on attributes. The approach is done by integrating Blockchain technology with CP-ABE for recording the attribute, preventing data tampering, and avoiding a single point of failure by optimizing the access control process using smart contracts to achieve lightweight authentication while fulfilling the high-efficiency needs of the IoT. The authors employed two types of Blockchain: the public Blockchain which is used for authentication, tagging servers, and storing user-defined

policies, whereas a consortium Blockchain is employed for storage, i.e. the hashes of transactions are kept thereafter, after users and devices have been validated. Although the Blockchain promises security and decentralization, it has scalability and cost issues.

The Blockchain-Based Attribute-Based Signcryption (BABSC) technique for cloud data sharing security was proposed and compared to comparable ABSC schemes in terms of storage and computation costs in [10]. Additionally, the authors integrate the Blockchain idea with attribute-based encryption to offer a safe data-sharing environment in the cloud. The proposed technique addresses the cloud computing security criteria of secrecy and unforgeability. Moreover, performance evaluations and simulation results demonstrate that the proposed technique is more efficient and feasible than others. Electronic health record sharing in the cloud using the Blockchain-Assisted Verifiable Outsourced Attribute-Based Signcryption (BVOABSC) scheme was proposed in [11]. BVOABSC is a secure sharing method that combines CP-ABSC and Blockchain technology. This approach can protect Electronic Health Records' (EHRs') confidentiality, accuracy, and integrity without depending on third parties. The system allows the Cloud Server (CS) to authenticate users' identities while respecting their privacy. Due to ABSC's properties, the proposed approach enables anonymous source authentication of EHRs, ensuring only authorized users submit EHRs, and protecting signers' privacy. It also ensures that the ciphertext size is constant and independent of the characteristics saving bandwidth and storage space in sharing scenarios. Furthermore, the proposed approach uses CS to perform most decryption operations, which reduces the user's computational load. The user may check the partial ciphertext created by CS, hence, the system meets the condition of verifiability. The proposed approach can withstand malevolent physicians and CS hacking of outsourced EHRs. Even if unscrupulous physicians conspire with cloud servers, the Blockchain is unchangeable. Given that most patients have several physicians creating their EHRs, the system adds a timestamp to each doctor, thus, assuring security. The drawbacks of this approach is that the operational process takes time and all physicians must be trained to use the system.

In order to solve the limitations of Blockchains, such as their limited throughput and high transaction fees, IOTA proposes using a new data format for the ledger and a different consensus algorithm. Authors in [12] presented the Decentralized Capability-based Access Control framework based on IOTA (DCACI). In DCACI, the subject sends an access request to an object owner, who assesses the access permissions to grant the subject, based on local authorization policies and issues an access token to the subject. Simultaneously, the owner adds the token to the Tangle, using MAM as the original copy. In the future, whenever the subject needs to get access to an object, an access request will be sent to the owner along with the token. Therefore, to authenticate the legitimacy of the supplied token, the owner compares it to the original on the Tangle. The DCACI system offers privacy and integrity for capability tokens that may be granted, updated, delegated, and revoked by device owners and users using IOTA's MAM technology. Although the proposed approach provides scalable and fine-grained access control for

IoT networks, it has a few shortcomings, including that it necessitates the establishment of a secure communication connection amongst subjects and object owners since requests and tokens are transmitted without being encrypted, making them more vulnerable to being disclosed to malicious or unauthorized individuals. Also, it only allows one-to-one access control, which implies that each subject must have its own token, making token management more difficult for large-scale IoT systems. Moreover, it does not specify how the authorization procedure should be implemented on the owner's side.

To address the above issues, a novel access control framework was proposed in [5]. The authors proposed an integrated scheme that combines IOTA with a hybrid of Capability-Based Access Control (CapBAC) and CP-ABE technology for IoT access control. The CP-ABE encrypts the token that controls access to a resource, and that token is stored in the IOTA Tangle. The authors demonstrated the scheme's viability by utilizing IOTA technology and IoT devices. The approach enables more secure, fine-grained, and scalable access control. It also allows object owners to grant access rights to many topics in a fraction of the time required by the DCACI scheme. The proposed scheme's performance was compared to DCACI's execution time. They also explored the scheme's scalability by incorporating additional regulations. The results reveal that execution time for each operation is related to the number of characteristics involved, and the number of policies has minimal influence on total execution time.

The above-mentioned works are compared in Table I with regard to a set of criteria to guarantee the efficiency and feasibility of the proposed solution. The first criterion is the use of DLT, which is a decentralized database managed by

multiple participants across multiple nodes that is used for recording asset transactions in which the transactions and their details are recorded in multiple places at the same time. The second criterion is the access control strategy, which is a security technique that regulates who sees or uses resources. The security requirement criteria field lists the proposed frameworks' security goals in order to meet their requirements. Then they were compared to the transaction fee criterion, which indicates whether the scheme must pay fees for its transaction process. Since the proposed solution is intended for IoT systems, the developed frameworks are compared to determine whether they are meant for IoT. Finally, each scheme's limitations are demonstrated. Several access control types have been deployed. Hybrid techniques were used in [8] to implement lightweight ABSC. However, their approach lacks confidentiality and integrity. Authors in [9-11], used different attribute-based access control types, such as CP-ABE, ABSC, and CP-ABSC. Their approaches ensure data tampering prevention, secure data sharing, and secure access control. Despite these features, each strategy has its own set of limitations, as shown in Table I. IOTA technology was used with CapBAC in [12] and with a hybrid of CapBAC and CP-ABE in [5]. Both frameworks guarantee fine-grained access control and support scalability, immutability, and fee-free transactions.

After reviewing all of the previously mentioned studies, it was noticed that there is an unfulfilled gap that deals with protecting the confidentiality of the data and its reliability from fraudulent activities, which can be achieved by signing and encrypting before uploading to the cloud, as well as delivering effective and scalable access control while preserving the signer's anonymity. This would be accomplished by combining IOTA and CP-ABSC technologies, which is the contribution of this paper.

TABLE I. CRITICAL ANALYSIS

Ref.	DLT	Access Control Strategy	Security requirements	Transaction Fees	Intended for IoT Systems	Limitations
[8]	Not applicable	ABSC with hybrid access policy (KPABS – CPABE)	Confidentiality. Ciphertext unforgeability. Fine-grained access control. CCA secure and CMA secure.	Not applicable	Yes	Does not ensure data confidentiality and integrity.
[9]	Public and private Blockchain	CP-ABE	Privacy and user authorization. Data tampering prevention and secure data sharing.	Yes	Yes	Suffers from scalability and cost issues.
[10]	Blockchain	ABSC	Secure data sharing over the cloud. Addresses confidentiality and integrity.	Yes	No	Requires improvement in the context of the computational cost of data encryption and authentication.
[11]	Blockchain	CP-ABSC	Data confidentiality, accuracy, and integrity. User authentication.	Yes	No	The operational process is time-consuming. Physicians need to be trained in using the system.
[12]	IOTA	CapBAC	Privacy and integrity for capability tokens. Fine-grained access control.	No	Yes	Required secure communication connection. Utilizes one-to-one access control.
[5]	IOTA	Hybrid of CapBAC and CP-ABE	Distributed, fee-less. Scalable and fine-grained access control.	No	Yes	Does not ensure data integrity and secure data sharing.
Proposed	IOTA	CP-ABSC	Data confidentiality and integrity. Scalable and fine-grained access control. User authentication. Ciphertext unforgeability	No	Yes	

III. PRELIMINARIES

A. IOTA

IOTA was introduced in 2015, deviating substantially from most of the existing cryptocurrencies, exhibiting features like quantum resistance, a ternary system, and replacing the Blockchain approach with a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) [13]. IOTA is a name derived from IoT and the word *iota*, which means "extremely small amount." The name was chosen to reflect the aim of IOTA, which is to connect things through microtransactions [14]. It is an innovative type of DLT designed for IoT access control. DLT does not use a central party in data storage. It secures the data into distributed databases without needing a central party to maintain them. An advanced cryptography technique is used to store records and transactions [15]. The Tangle stores transactions as vertices and links them with edges that represent the approval of previous transactions, using cryptographic signatures to secure the data. This technique aids in acquiring high throughput in recording the new incoming data [5]. The characteristics of IOTA are:

Transactions are fee-less since they are miner-free and do not require any involvement from miners [12]. The IOTA Tangle delivers scalability and authenticity as well as high-speed transactions. It is faster and more powerful to process new transactions [18]. IOTA is a decentralized technology [5]. IOTA integrates a data communication protocol called Masked Authentication Messaging (MAM). This protocol uses the Tangle network and provides an ideal solution for access control. The MAM protocol protects the transactions from tampering. It encrypts the messages before adding the transactions to the Tangle [16]. Each MAM transaction has an address that any peer can use to refer to the transaction. MAM transactions issued by the same peer are chronologically connected to establish a channel (i.e. a chain of transactions). A signature of the issuer is also linked to every MAM transaction, allowing subscribers to verify the issuer's validity (authenticated messaging). By subscribing to each other's channels, peers can safely share data across the Tangle using MAM [4].

B. Ciphertext-Policy Attribute-Based Signcryption (CP-ABSC)

Access control refers to the process of restricting access to only authorized parties in order to get access to a certain resource [12]. Access policies specify who may access what resources. Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC) is a type of dynamic, fine-grained, and flexible access control in which attribute authorities give identities or responsibilities to a group of attributes, thereby avoiding the need to construct separate access control lists for each entity in the system. It successfully simplifies access control since there are fewer characteristics compared to the number of users in the system. ABE was first introduced in [7]. It is a vision and extension of public-key encryption that enables users to encrypt and decrypt data depending on user attributes. ABE is a crucial tool for tackling the issue of secure data sharing and access control. ABE is a significant improvement over traditional public key cryptography because it achieves flexible one-to-many encryption rather than one-to-one encryption, in which

ciphertexts encrypt a specific user. Users' private keys and ciphertexts, on the other hand, will be associated with a set of characteristics or policies that govern them. If a match exists between the user's private key and the ciphertext, the user would indeed decrypt the ciphertext. ABE is categorized into two categories [18]: Key-Policy ABE (KP-ABE) [4] and CP-ABE [18, 19]. The KP-ABE links the access policies to users' private keys while using attribute sets to annotate ciphertexts. On the other hand, in CP-ABE, each ciphertext is associated with an access policy, and each user's private key is associated with an attribute set, therefore, it is considered an ideal choice for data owners who want to control who can decipher their data [8].

Attribute-Based Signatures (ABS) was proposed in [20] as a new type of digital signature. ABS is a cryptographic primitive that enables a signing entity to generate a signature with fine-grained control over identifying information. A valid ABS signature certifies that a particular user, for whom attributes stratify the predicate, attested the message without exposing further information [21]. Therefore, it anonymously provides message authenticity, which implies that colluding parties are not able to pool their attributes together. The concept of Attribute-Based Signcryption (ABSC) [22] merges the features of encryption and signature in a single phase, generating an effective approach to achieving security requirements including authentication, data confidentiality, data integrity, and non-repudiation. Additionally, it has a lower computational cost as compared to the traditional signature strategy than encryption strategies. ABSC consists of four algorithms [10], as follows:

- **Setup:** It is configured by a Trusted Authority (TA) who generates a master secret key (msk) and public parameters (pk) using a security parameter (k). The user will receive the (pk). However, the (msk) will be kept private.
- **Keygen:** this algorithm generates the private key (Sk), and the verification key (Vk) based on the user's attributes set (S) and the input (msk) (S).
- **Signcrypt:** is run by the administrator and takes two inputs: plaintext (M) and private key (Sk) to output the ciphertext (CT).
- **Designcrypt:** is run by the users. It takes the (Sk), the (CT), and (S) as inputs to produce (M).

In this paper, an efficient and flexible approach termed as Ciphertext Policy Attribute-Based Signcryption (CP-ABSC) will be used to accomplish fine-grained access control, confidentiality, authenticity, unforgeability, and sender privacy concurrently.

IV. THE PROPOSED SCHEME

Protecting data from unauthorized access is critical in preventing unlawful access to information and resources and safeguarding them from any attack in order to obtain the trust of the concerned parties and guarantee that their data are secure from any breaches. As a suggested solution to this issue, a scheme is proposed that develops a mechanism that offers

efficient and secure access control. It employs IOTA technology in conjunction with CP-ABSC technology to provide a protected access control scheme with finer granularity, flexibility, and scalability. More precisely, the proposed approach uses CP-ABSC to sign and encrypt access rights before recording them in the IOTA Tangle. Furthermore, the data will be encrypted before being uploaded to the cloud server, ensuring that they are secure from any security breaches. Additionally, it is ensured that the user is authorized to access the data by properly determining the CP-ABSC policies. Therefore, the proposed scheme can achieve fine-grained access control and implement the principle of least privilege. As demonstrated in Figure 1, which simplifies how the proposed system works, it has two types of users, the data owner, and the data user. The data owner is anyone who owns environmental monitoring data, whether it is a government agency or an individual who wants to monitor the environment around him, whether indoors or outdoors, while a data user is anyone who wants to view and access this data.

- The data owner can define the policies and access permissions that must be followed when accessing the data in the form of a small object named token, which can then be signcryptured using CP-ABSC and be sent to the Tangle.
- The data user can submit a request for access to the data along with the appropriate token (after fetching it from the Tangle) to demonstrate that he is authorized to access that data.

Fig. 1. The proposed scheme.

A. Token Structure

In the proposed system, Tangle is used to store tokens after being signcryptured using CP-ABSC, which contains an attribute set that encompasses the policies and access permissions that the user must meet in order to access the data. A token is a JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) object issued by data owners that contains an identifier (ID), the issuer's name, the policy, and the access rights. The token will be fetched from the Tangle by those who meet these attributes and have the decryption keys, and anyone else will not be able to download or use it. Figure 2 shows an example of a token that will be

available to those with the role of staff who want to access air quality data.

```

token #1:{
  ID: 1938484234
  Issuer: Afnan Hussein
  Policy: role: staff
  Access rights:
    [
      Type of data: Air Quality
      action : read/write
    ]
}

```

Fig. 2. Token example.

B. System Functions

The proposed system intends to assist the data owner in preserving the integrity and reliability of his information and restricting the access to them, ensuring that only authorized data users have access to it. The functions of the proposed system are briefly described below:

- User Identification (Login): users must enter a valid login credential to enroll in the system, otherwise, an error message will be displayed.
- Generation and Protection of Access Tokens: The data owner creates tokens and associates them with the data that contain the permissions required for access. Then, CP-ABSC will be used to signcrypt the token before storing it in the Tangle.
- Retrieval and Decryption of Access Token: The data user can obtain the token from the Tangle and decrypt it before sending a request to access the data. If the data user is authorized to download the token from the Tangle, then he can easily decrypt and view the token for the selected date.
- Send Access Request: The data user sends an access request along with the downloaded token to the data owner to ensure its authorization to access the data.
- Access Requests Validation: The data owner compares the received token to the original one stored in the Tangle and prompts the user if they match. Otherwise, he denies access.

V. SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

A web-based application named Management of Environmental Monitoring Data was developed that has a flexible, simple, and convenient user interface, while making the process of preserving and maintaining access to the data smoother. To develop the proposed system, an HP laptop was used with the following characteristics: Windows 11 Home Edition, 16GB RAM, Intel Core i7 10th generation processor. The Laravel framework was used to build and design the web application using the model-view-controller architectural pattern, along with MetaMask, which is a software cryptocurrency wallet, used to send the data to the Tangle through the interaction between the web application and the smart contract, as well as Remix for writing, compiling, and debugging the solidity code of the smart contract (that is used

to store the data that will be sent to the Tangle). Additionally, the IOTA-EVM network was used for setting up an IOTA network in order to send data transactions. When the data are sent from the web application to the Tangle, their transactions can be shown using <https://explorer.wasp.sc.iota.org/>. The proposed scheme aims to protect the resources' integrity and reliability while also restricting access to them. Therefore, the user must enter valid login information using the email address and password they used to register for IoT-based environmental monitoring devices in order to log in to the system, as shown in Figure 3. If the user enters his credentials correctly, the system will redirect him to his dashboard, otherwise, it will display an error message. There are two types of users: data owners and data users, and the information displayed on the dashboard will differ depending on the type of user. The data owner's dashboard gives him access to all the downloaded environmental data from the cloud and provides capabilities for accessing requests and creating tokens. On the other hand, the data user is able to view the data that he has previously been granted access to, as well as send new requests to data owners for access to other types of environmental data.

Fig. 3. Login page.

A. Generation and Protection of the Access Token

During the token generation step, the data owner will create tokens and link them to the data, which contain the policy and permission required for access. As illustrated in Figure 4, the token will determine the data type, such as air quality, humidity, and temperature. Additionally, it specifies the user role, indicating whether the user is a staff member or an ordinary user, and the permission type, indicating whether the user has read-only, write-only, or read-and-write access rights. The data owner then signcrypts the token with CP-ABSC and stores it in the Tangle via a MetaMask connection.

B. Retrieval and Decryption of the Access Token

As displayed in Figure 5, before sending a request for access to the data, the data user must first obtain a token from the Tangle and decrypt it with his own key. Since the proposed system employs CP-ABSC, only authorized users who match the policies that the data owner specified during the token generation step can download the tokens.

Fig. 4. Token creation page.

Fig. 5. Fetched token details.

C. Send Access Request

The data user can gain access to the data by submitting a request to the data owner requesting authorization and clearly stating the type of data he desires to view and the action he seeks to take with that data, as shown in Figure 6. More importantly, the appropriate token should be attached to this request, which has been downloaded during the Retrieval of the Access Token step.

Fig. 6. Sending request page.

D. Access Request Validation

The data owner can view the upcoming users' access requests, examine the request's details (the request details should include the user information such as name and role), and verify the attached token against the original one. Consequently, upon these details, the request will be approved or denied by the data owner as presented in Figure 7.

Fig. 7. Access request details.

As demonstrated in Figure 8, by pressing the validate token button, the token attached to the request is compared to the original one stored in the Tangle. If they match, a suitable message will be displayed, allowing the data owner to approve the request. However, if the token has been altered or counterfeited, it will be known due to the Tangle’s immutability, resulting in a message stating that they are incompatible, as shown in Figure 9. As a result, the request will be denied by the data owner.

Fig. 8. Token matched.

Fig. 9. Token not matched.

VI. PERFORMANCE RESULTS

In this section, the proposed system was evaluated for throughput performance in terms of execution time. Different target users were selected to use and assess the system. For easier evaluation, the tasks were divided for each user and the amount of time it takes for the user to accomplish each task was recorded, as illustrated in Table II (the time indicated is the maximum time that can be used to complete these tasks, with the age of the user affecting these values). For performing the testing tasks, there are two users: a data owner who is in charge of environmental data, setting privileges, creating tokens, maintaining, and managing account requests, and the data user, who accesses the system through login and uses tokens in order to gain access to the data.

TABLE II. SYSTEM PERFORMANCE BASED ON USER TASKS

User	Tasks	Time (s)	Details
Data owner - Data user	Login	15-30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Login • View data
Data owner	Create and store token in the Tangle	20-50	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create token • Fill out the form • Submit the form • Verify token details before sending to Tangle • Signcrypt and save to Tangle
	View request list	25-40	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Choose request list • Click on any received request • View details • Verify the received token with the original one • Accept (or deny) the request
Data user	Send request	15-30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Send a request • Fill out the form • Download the token and view its details • Attach it with the request • Submit form

Figure 10 represents how much time each user spends during the system testing process. Figure 10 represents the time spent while executing the functions of the data owner. Time is represented in seconds (s) through the login step, creating and storing the token, and viewing the request list. The time through the login step was between 15 and 25 s, during creating and storing the token it was between 20 and 30 s and during the execution of the view request list step, it was between 25 and 35 s. Figure 11 shows the data user’s execution time through the login process and sending requests for accessing data. The executed time was approximately 20 s during the login step whereas it was between 15–20 s during the sending request.

Fig. 10. Data owner execution time.

Fig. 11. Data user execution time.

VII. SECURITY EVALUATION

In order to ensure that the proposed scheme achieves security, confidentiality, and fine-grained access control, several test cases were created to evaluate the system’s security against these scenarios. The token is used in the proposed system to define the policies and permissions that the data user must satisfy in order to ensure that he is authorized to access the data. Therefore, anyone who does not meet these attribute sets will be unable to download the token from the Tangle and, as a result, will be unable to use it to send a request for data access. However, attackers may attempt to commit fraud in order to obtain the token. Various test cases were run on the proposed system to ensure that it meets the security requirements of the token, and the outcomes are displayed in Tables III-VI.

TABLE III. TEST CASE #1

Test Case #1	Create and store tokens in the Tangle.
Description	The data owner creates the token and signcrypts it before sending it to the Tangle. Additionally, to store data through Metamask to the Tangle, they must be converted from text to hexadecimal.
Outcome	The token in the proposed system will be signencrypted using CP-ABSC before being converted to hexadecimal, making it completely secure and non-falsifiable.
Result	

TABLE IV. TEST CASE #2

Test Case #2	The data user sends a valid token.
Description	The case of a valid user who is able to decrypt the token and send it with a request to access data.
Outcome	The attached token will be compared to the original one stored in the Tangle. If they match, a message stating that they are identical will be displayed.
Result	

TABLE V. TEST CASE #3

Test Case#3	A data user/attacker sends an invalid token.
Description	Whenever an invalid token is sent, it has been modified by a data user with malicious intent or by an attacker who stole another valid user’s information.
Outcome	If the token has been forged or altered after being downloaded and decrypted from the Tangle, the changes made to the token will be discovered since the Tangle is not subject to change. Therefore, after comparison to the original one, a message will be displayed to clarify that the tokens do not match.
Result	

TABLE VI. TEST CASE #4

Test Case #4	An attacker or ineligible user seeks to obtain a token.
Description	An attacker or an unauthorized user attempts to obtain the token from the Tangle in order to gain access to the data.
Outcome	The use of CP-ABSC technology on the token prevents unauthorized individuals from accessing the token because it can be fetched by those legitimate users who meet the attribute set written in the token and have the decryption keys. Thus, illegitimate attempts to access the token will be detected, and a warning message will appear.
Result	

It was demonstrated in the previous test cases that the proposed system is secure, it protects users’ information and preserves data confidentiality by maintaining the token’s security while also preserving the anonymity of the signer’s identity. The key to its success is IOTA technology and CP-ABSC technology.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The number of devices deployed in IoT systems is growing exponentially. Some of these devices conduct environmental monitoring. As the industrial and infrastructure frameworks have grown rapidly, environmental monitoring has become more important. Because IoT systems frequently handle sensitive data, proper access control is essential to prevent unauthorized access. Numerous studies have been carried out to create ways to protect these data while simultaneously guaranteeing user authorization. These studies have combined various kinds of ABSC with Blockchain and IOTA to implement various sorts of access control. Nevertheless, their approaches suffer from several shortcomings, such as scalability and cost difficulties, failing to guarantee confidentiality, integrity, and secure sharing of the data. IOTA and CP-ABSC were integrated into the proposed system to cover this issue. The proposed system uses the CP-ABSC to sign and encrypt the access privileges before storing them in the IOTA Tangle. Additionally, the data will be encrypted before being sent to the cloud server, ensuring protection against breaches. Moreover, the correct CP-ABSC policies are determined to ensure that the user has appropriate permissions to access the resources. The integrity and confidentiality of the data and resources collected by IoT devices are preserved by employing the above approach, which creates a more secure, granular, and scalable access control system.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Zafar, G. Miraj, R. Baloch, D. Murtaza, and K. Arshad, "An IoT Based Real-Time Environmental Monitoring System Using Arduino and Cloud Service," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 3238–3242, Aug. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2144>.
- [2] Y. B. Zikria, R. Ali, M. K. Afzal, and S. W. Kim, "Next-Generation Internet of Things (IoT): Opportunities, Challenges, and Solutions," *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 4, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 1174, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s21041174>.

- [3] A. N. Chaudhari and G. A. Kulkarni, "IOT based environmental pollution monitoring system," *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, vol. 4, no. 6, pp. 1823–1829, Jun. 2017.
- [4] R. Nakanishi, Y. Zhang, M. Sasabe, and S. Kasahara, "IOTA-Based Access Control Framework for the Internet of Things," in *2020 2nd Conference on Blockchain Research & Applications for Innovative Networks and Services (BRAINS)*, Paris, France, Sep. 2020, pp. 87–95, <https://doi.org/10.1109/BRAINS49436.2020.9223293>.
- [5] Y. Zhang, R. Nakanishi, M. Sasabe, and S. Kasahara, "Combining IOTA and Attribute-Based Encryption for Access Control in the Internet of Things," *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 15, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 5053, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s21155053>.
- [6] G. Lin, Y. Xia, C. Ying, and Z. Sun, "F2P-ABS: A Fast and Secure Attribute-Based Signature for Mobile Platforms," *Security and Communication Networks*, vol. 2019, Dec. 2019, Art. no. e5380710, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/5380710>.
- [7] N. A. Alsharif, S. Mishra, and M. Alshehri, "IDS in IoT using Machine Learning and Blockchain," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 11197–11203, Aug. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5992>.
- [8] J. Yu, S. Liu, S. Wang, Y. Xiao, and B. Yan, "LH-ABSC: A Lightweight Hybrid Attribute-Based Signcryption Scheme for Cloud-Fog-Assisted IoT," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 7, no. 9, pp. 7949–7966, Sep. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/JIOT.2020.2992288>.
- [9] S. Y. A. Zaidi *et al.*, "An Attribute-Based Access Control for IoT Using Blockchain and Smart Contracts," *Sustainability*, vol. 13, no. 19, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 10556, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su131910556>.
- [10] N. Eltayieb, R. Elhabob, A. Hassan, and F. Li, "A blockchain-based attribute-based signcryption scheme to secure data sharing in the cloud," *Journal of Systems Architecture*, vol. 102, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 101653, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sysarc.2019.101653>.
- [11] X. Yang, T. Li, W. Xi, A. Chen, and C. Wang, "A Blockchain-Assisted Verifiable Outsourced Attribute-Based Signcryption Scheme for EHRs Sharing in the Cloud," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 170713–170731, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3025060>.
- [12] S. K. Pinjala and K. M. Sivalingam, "DCACI: A Decentralized Lightweight Capability Based Access Control Framework using IOTA for Internet of Things," in *2019 IEEE 5th World Forum on Internet of Things (WF-IoT)*, Limerick, Ireland, Apr. 2019, pp. 13–18, <https://doi.org/10.1109/WF-IoT.2019.8767356>.
- [13] O. Lamtzidis and J. Gialelis, "An IOTA Based Distributed Sensor Node System," in *2018 IEEE Globecom Workshops (GC Wkshps)*, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates, Sep. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/GLOCOMW.2018.8644153>.
- [14] "What does IOTA stand for?," *Quora*. <https://www.quora.com/What-does-IOTA-stand-for>.
- [15] M. M. Akhtar, M. Z. Khan, M. A. Ahad, A. Noorwali, D. R. Rizvi, and C. Chakraborty, "Distributed ledger technology based robust access control and real-time synchronization for consumer electronics," *PeerJ Computer Science*, vol. 7, Jun. 2021, Art. no. e566, <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.566>.
- [16] P. C. Bartolomeu, E. Vieira, and J. Ferreira, "IOTA Feasibility and Perspectives for Enabling Vehicular Applications," in *2018 IEEE Globecom Workshops (GC Wkshps)*, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates, Sep. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/GLOCOMW.2018.8644201>.
- [17] V. Goyal, O. Pandey, A. Sahai, and B. Waters, "Attribute-based encryption for fine-grained access control of encrypted data," in *Proceedings of the 13th ACM conference on Computer and communications security*, New York, NY, USA, Jul. 2006, pp. 89–98, <https://doi.org/10.1145/1180405.1180418>.
- [18] J. Bethencourt, A. Sahai, and B. Waters, "Ciphertext-Policy Attribute-Based Encryption," in *2007 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP '07)*, Berkeley, CA, USA, Feb. 2007, pp. 321–334, <https://doi.org/10.1109/SP.2007.11>.
- [19] A. Lewko, T. Okamoto, A. Sahai, K. Takashima, and B. Waters, "Fully Secure Functional Encryption: Attribute-Based Encryption and (Hierarchical) Inner Product Encryption," in *Advances in Cryptology – EUROCRYPT 2010*, 2010, pp. 62–91, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-13190-5_4.
- [20] H. K. Maji, M. Prabhakaran, and M. Rosulek, "Attribute-Based Signatures," in *Topics in Cryptology – CT-RSA 2011*, 2011, pp. 376–392, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-19074-2_24.
- [21] G. Lin, Y. Xia, C. Ying, and Z. Sun, "F2P-ABS: A Fast and Secure Attribute-Based Signature for Mobile Platforms," *Security and Communication Networks*, vol. 2019, Dec. 2019, Art. no. e5380710, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/5380710>.
- [22] Y. Zheng, "Digital signcryption or how to achieve $\text{cost}(\text{signature} \& \text{encryption}) \ll \text{cost}(\text{signature}) + \text{cost}(\text{encryption})$," in *Advances in Cryptology – CRYPTO '97*, 1997, pp. 165–179, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BFb0052234>.

Count Data Modeling for Predicting Crash Severity on Indian Highways

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ABSTRACT

This study collected data on road accidents for the years 2016-2020 for the NH-48 highway in Maharashtra, India to model their conditions. Road crash data models were developed using 70% of actual data for training and 30% for testing purposes. Negative binomial regression modeling was used to predict crash fatalities. The results showed that the factors that affected the fatality of road crashes were head-on-collision, friction, time zone, and weather conditions of the crash. The developed models were validated and tested using log-likelihood, AIC, BIC, MAD, MSE, RMSE, and MAPE values. Head-on-collision, AM, PM, light rain, mist/fog, heavy rain, fine, and cloudy were positively associated with the fatality of road crashes, while friction was negatively associated. The developed models can be used to predict the fatality/non-fatality of road crashes and implement road safety strategies on highways to reduce them.

Keywords-crash; data; modeling; NH-48; road safety; India

I. INTRODUCTION

Road crashes result from a variety of factors, such as road geometry, road traffic, vehicle conditions, human faults, etc. As these factors include a wide variety of subfactors, road crash analysis becomes a complex phenomenon to achieve a single-point solution. India is ranked first in the world in terms of road crash deaths [1]. Between 2020 and 2021, there was an increase of 12.6% in road crashes, 16.9% in deaths, and 10.39% in injuries [2].

A. Road Crash Data Modeling in India

In [3], a correlation was discovered between highway geometric parameters, traffic parameters, and crash rates for two-lane non-urban highways, showing a positive connection between the volume of heavy vehicles, speed, and crash rates, while shoulder and lane widths showed a negative relationship with crash rates. In [4], a random parameter model was developed for rural highways in India using accident data for 3 years on a 200 km highway segment. In [5], a method was proposed for road safety audits on four-lane national highways using multiple and nonlinear regression analysis. Additionally, an ANN model was developed with MATLAB R2009b neural network toolbox to identify safety parameters that minimize accidents in selected sections of the highway. In [6], road geometry and traffic variables were investigated in motorcycle crashes using a statistical technique called zero-inflated negative binomial regression for the NH-6 highway. The accident prediction model used accidents per year per km as a

response variable and other data as input variables. In [7], eight national and state highways in Haryana were selected to develop accident prediction models with the help of 2-6 years of accident data, road geometry, and traffic data. Two modeling approaches were used, the Fixed/Random Effect Negative Binomial (FENB/RENB) and the M5 model, which is a binary decision tree learner used to predict a response variable and has linear regression functions at the terminal (leaf) nodes. The M5 model tree method was suggested as an alternative to RENB.

In [8], the effect of geometric design characteristics on the frequency of crashes on divided highways under various flow conditions was studied, using statistical modeling approaches such as Poisson and negative binomial regression. This study concluded that the negative binomial is an appropriate tool for predicting road crashes in this context. In [9], a crash prediction model was developed to identify the impact of accidents on the national economy. Crash data from a national highway during 2009-2012 were collected and linear regression analysis was used to suggest remedial measures to improve road safety. In [10], the influential parameters that resulted in fatal crashes were studied on three national highways of 2, 4, and 6 lanes, using logistic regression modeling. Influential variables were the number of lanes, the type of collision, and the number of vehicles. In [11], a regression model was developed to determine the relationship between the deaths of all road users by different modes of travel. The results showed that cycling, walking, and public transport systems had a low probability of fatal injuries, whereas two-wheelers, cars, and buses were at

higher risk of fatalities. In [12], a generalized linear model was developed for crash prediction and accident hotspot detection on rural highways. The model showed that average daily traffic and average spot speed were the key factors responsible for road accidents.

B. Road Crash Data Modeling in Other Countries

In [13], crash-prediction models were developed for four-lane median-divided roads in Italy using accident data from 1999 to 2003, and statistical analysis was performed with the help of a negative multinomial regression model. The findings of this study were separate for both curves and tangents. Length, Annual Average Daily Traffic (AADT), and $1/\text{radius}$ were the significant variables for the curves, while for the tangents it was the junctions along with length and AADT. In [14], a generalized linear modeling method was used to develop crash prediction models for Italy's rural motorways, using 2001-2005 crash data and developing separate models for total and severe crashes using a negative binomial distribution. This study considered traffic volume, speed, alignment, design, sight distance, cross-section, and interchange ramps as explanatory variables. In [15], the parameters that contributed to fatal hit-and-run crashes in California, USA, were identified, using a logistic regression approach. The parameters were traffic control devices, speed limits, roadway profiles, and lighting conditions to reduce hit-and-run cases. In [16], differences in the severity of driver injuries between single and multiple-vehicle accidents of trucks were investigated, using 10-year accident data from a rural highway and a mixed logit modeling technique. The study concluded that there was a substantial difference between impacts on the severity of driver injuries in single/multiple vehicle accidents due to a variety of variables, such as roadway, driver, and environmental and vehicle characteristics. In [17], a crash data analysis was performed in Riyadh City, Saudi Arabia, considering a logit modeling approach, showing that a crash involving multiple vehicles is less severe than a crash involving a single vehicle.

In [18], Generalized Linear Modeling (GLM) and Geographically Weighted Poisson Regression (GWPR) were compared using crash data from 58 counties in California, showing that GWPR performed better in the specific context. In [19], the severity of road accidents per vehicle type was investigated in Greece, using lognormal regression analysis and concluding that weather conditions and night increased the risk of accidents. In [20], the impact of variable speed limits on road safety was studied using decision trees. In [21], the Negative Binomial-Multinomial Logit Fractional Split (NB-MNLFS) method was presented as an alternative to the most common modeling technique for unobserved heterogeneity. This method was compared to the multivariate random-parameter negative binomial model, showing excellent potential. In [22], accidents involving driving under the consumption of drugs/alcohol and resulting in fatalities were studied, using data from the forensic toxicology databases of the Norwegian road traffic crash registries in 2005–2015 and logistic regression, and finding that risk factors, such as not using seat belts or helmets, driving with invalid licenses, and overspeeding, were important.

In [23], time series modeling was used to study the relationship between police enforcement, traffic accidents, and traffic violations. The results showed that traffic violations and crashes had weekly variations and were affected by weather and holiday conditions, while the police patrol time was not affected. In [24], the combined effect of lighting and weather conditions was studied in single-vehicle accidents in Scotland, using data on the severity of injuries from 2016 and 2017. The results showed that all the parameters had different effects on the severity of the crashes. In [25], a mobile application system was proposed to report road accidents and driver overspeed awareness to improve road safety. In [26], a study was conducted on driver characteristics and their impact on road safety. The driver's characteristics were assessed by an actual driving experiment with a safety expert and responses to a questionnaire. A simple linear regression model was developed, showing that driving experience and skill, headway, and defensive driving affected driving performance. In [27], a survey was conducted to determine the local public opinion on crashes, showing that human and road factors have the most significant impact, with negligent driving and overspeeding being the main causes of road traffic accidents.

II. METHOD

Figure 1 shows the method used to achieve the study objectives, presenting its 3 major stages: Road crash data collection, modeling fatality/non-fatality of crashes, and validation of the models.

Fig. 1. Method.

A. Road Crash Data Collection

Data were collected from the National Highways Authority of India (NHAI) between 2016 and 2020 for the NH-48 rural national highway, which passes through the state of Maharashtra and has a length of approximately 265 km, considering both sides of the highway.

B. Modeling the Fatality/Non-fatality of the Crashes

The road crash data collected were statistically studied and, based on their distribution, a negative binomial regression model was identified to predict the fatality/non-fatality of crashes in the study area. Negative binomial regression is similar to regular multiple regression, except that the dependent variable (y) is an observed count that follows the negative binomial distribution. Thus, the possible values of y were the non-negative integers: 0, 1, 2, 3, and so on. Negative binomial regression is a generalization of Poisson regression, which loosens the restrictive assumption that the variance is equal to

the mean made by the Poisson model. The mathematical form of the negative binomial regression is as follows:

$$\ln(y) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_i + \dots + \beta_m X_{im} \quad (1)$$

C. Validation of the Models

The developed models were validated based on log-likelihood, Bayesian Information Criteria (BIC), Akaike's Information Criteria (AIC), Mean Absolute Deviation (MAD), Mean Square Error (MSE), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) values. Table I shows the criteria used for the validation of the models.

TABLE I. MODEL VALIDATION CRITERIA

No.	Parameter	Significance
1	Log-likelihood	Highest
2	AIC	Lowest
3	BIC	Lowest
4	MAD	Lowest
5	MSE	Lowest
6	RMSE	Lowest
7	MAPE	0-10 %= High precision
		10-20%= Good
		20-50%= Reasonable
		More than 50%= Inaccurate

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data were divided into 2 parts, namely training and validation sets. The training data were the 70% of the actual data and were used to train the models, which were then validated on the 30% of the actual data. Four models were developed, which are discussed in detail below.

A. Model 1

The independent variable selected here was the nature of the crash, which was classified as head-on-collision, overturning, rear-end-collision, friction, etc. Figure 2 shows the parameter estimates of Model 1. It can be seen that intercepts B = 2 (head-on-collision) and B = 6 (friction) are the only significant parameters of the nature of the crash. The equation of the model is:

$$\ln(y) = -2.067 + (0.474 \times HeadOnCollision) - (2.263 \times Friction) \quad (2)$$

Parameter	B	Std. Error	95% Wald Confidence Interval		Hypothesis Test			95% Wald Confidence Interval for Exp(B)		
			Lower	Upper	Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	Lower	Upper
(intercept)	-2.067	0.1906	-2.441	-1.694	117.602	1	0.00000	0.127	0.00087	0.00184
[B=1]	0.545	0.3713	-0.183	1.273	0.02153	1	0.000142	1.724	0.00833	0.03570
[B=2]	0.474	0.2355	0.012	0.935	0.04050	1	0.000044	1.606	0.01012	0.02548
[B=3]	0.433	0.2352	-0.028	0.894	3.386	1	0.000665	1.541	0.00972	0.02444
[B=4]	0.768	0.6787	-0.562	2.098	1.281	1	0.00258	2.155	0.00570	0.08151
[B=5]	-26.138	941165.0442	-1844675.726	1844623.455	0.00000	1	0.001000	4.461E-12	0.00000	a
[B=6]	-2.263	1.0244	-4.271	-0.256	4.882	1	0.000027	0.104	0.000014	0.000774
[B=7]	-26.136 ^b							4.461E-12	0.00000	0.00000
[B=8]	0 ^c									1
(Scale)	1 ^d									
(Negative binomial)	1 ^d									

Dependent Variable: Fatal or Non Fatal
Model: (Intercept), B

Fig. 2. Model 1 parameter estimates.

B. Model 2

The independent variable selected here was the time zone of the crash, which was classified as AM and PM. Figure 3 shows the parameter estimates of Model 2. It can be seen that the intercept Zone = 0 (AM) is the only significant parameter from the time zone of the crash. The equation of this model is:

$$\ln(y) = -1.993 + [0.535 \times TimeZone (AM/PM)] \quad (3)$$

Parameter	B	Std. Error	95% Wald Confidence Interval		Hypothesis Test			95% Wald Confidence Interval for Exp(B)		
			Lower	Upper	Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	Lower	Upper
(intercept)	-1.99	0.1111	-2.211	-1.775	321.572	1	0.000	0.136	0.110	0.169
[Zone=0]	535	0	0.210	1	10.388	1	0.001	1.708	1.233	2.365
[Zone=1]	0 ^a							1		
(Scale)	1 ^b									
(Negative binomial)	1 ^b									

Dependent Variable: Fatal or Non Fatal
Model: (Intercept), Zone

Fig. 3. Model 2 parameter estimates.

C. Model 3

The independent variable selected here was the weather condition of the crash, which was classified as fine, cloudy, light rain, heavy rain, etc. Figure 4 shows the parameter estimates for the model. It can be seen that the intercepts H = 1 (fine), H = 2 (mist/fog), H = 3 (cloudy), H = 4 (light rain), and H = 5 (heavy rain), were the only significant parameters of the weather condition of the crash. This model is described as:

$$\ln(y) = -27.122 + 25.180 \times Fine + 25.823 \times Mist/Fog + 25.550 \times Cloudy + 24.963 \times LightRain + 25.513 \times HeavyRain \quad (4)$$

Parameter	B	Std. Error	95% Wald Confidence Interval		Hypothesis Test			95% Wald Confidence Interval for Exp(B)		
			Lower	Upper	Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	Lower	Upper
(intercept)	-27.122	0.3757	-27.859	-26.386	5212.358	1	0.00000	1.663E-12	7.965E-13	3.473E-12
[H=1]	25.180	0.3965	24.403	26.958	4032.531	1	0.00000	8.624E+10	3.96E+10	1.876E+11
[H=2]	25.823	0.4140	25.011	26.634	3889.730	1	0.00000	1.640E+11	7.283E+10	3.691E+11
[H=3]	25.550	0.4216	24.724	26.376	3673.130	1	0.00000	1.248E+11	5.461E+10	2.851E+11
[H=4]	24.963	0.4642	24.053	25.873	2891.755	1	0.00000	6.937E+10	2.793E+10	1.723E+11
[H=5]	25.513	0.6642	24.211	26.815	1475.537	1	0.00000	1.202E+11	3.27E+10	4.420E+11
[H=10]	25.075 ^a							7.158E+10	0.00000	0.00000
[H=11]	0 ^b							1		
(Scale)	1 ^c									
(Negative binomial)	1 ^c									

Dependent Variable: Fatal or Non Fatal
Model: (Intercept), H

Fig. 4. Model 3 parameter estimates.

D. Model 4

The independent variables selected here were the nature of the crash, which was classified as head-on-collision, overturning, rear-end-collision, friction, etc., and its time zone, which was divided into AM and PM. Figure 5 shows the parameter estimates of the model. It can be seen that the intercepts Zone = 0 (AM) and B = 6 (Friction) are the only significant parameters from the time zone and the nature of the crash, respectively. The equation of the model is:

$$\ln(y) = -2.239 + [0.496 \times \text{TimeZone}(AM/PM)] + (-2.266 \times \text{Friction}) \tag{5}$$

Parameter	B	Std. Error	95% Wald Confidence Interval		Hypothesis Test			Exp(B)	95% Wald Confidence Interval	
			Lower	Upper	Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.		Lower	Upper
			(Intercept)	-2.239	0.2020	-2.635	-1.843		122.821	1
[Zone=0]	0.496	0.1677	0.167	0.824	8.740	1	0.003	1.642	1.182	2.281
[Zone=1]	0 ^a							1.000		
[B=1]	0.475	0.3735	-0.257	1.207	1.617	1	0.204	1.608	0.773	3.344
[B=2]	0.443	0.2365	-0.021	0.906	3.509	1	0.061	1.557	0.980	2.475
[B=3]	0.397	0.2363	-0.066	0.860	2.287	1	0.093	1.488	0.936	2.364
[B=4]	0.674	0.6827	-0.664	2.012	0.975	1	0.323	1.962	0.515	7.480
[B=5]	-26.235	937898.1100	-1838272.752	1838220.281	0.000	1	1.000	4.04E-12	0.000	b
[B=6]	-2.266	1.0249	-4.275	-0.258	4.890	1	0.027	0.104	0.014	0.773
[B=7]	-25.964 ^c							5.3E-12	0.000	0.000
[B=8]	0 ^a							1.000		
(Scale)	1 ^d									
(Negative binomial)	1 ^d									

Dependent Variable: Fatal or Non Fatal
Model: (Intercept), Zone, B

Fig. 5. Model 4 parameter estimates.

The results of this study state that the nature of the crash and weather conditions are the most important factors associated with the crashes. The nature of the crash and weather conditions were also associated in [10, 21, 23, 24]. Negative binomial regression modeling is the best-suited tool for crash prediction modeling [8].

IV. MODEL VALIDATION

The four developed models to predict the fatality or non-fatality of road crashes, shown in (2)-(5), were validated using the criteria shown in Table I. Table II shows the validation parameters for the four models. Model 4 showed the highest log-likelihood and the lowest AIC and MAD values among the others, being -477.904, 973.807, and 0.1597, respectively. Model 2 showed the lowest BIC, MSE, and MAPE values among all models, being 992.261, 0.132, and 0.1303, respectively. Model 1 had the lowest RMSE value among all models, being 0.359.

TABLE II. MODEL VALIDATION PARAMETERS

Model	Log-Likelihood	AIC	BIC	MAD	MSE	RMSE	MAPE
1	-482.220	980.441	1019.884	0.2515	0.1289	0.359	0.1306
2	-489.200	982.400	992.261	0.269	0.132	0.363	0.1303
3	-487.591	989.181	1023.695	0.256	0.1342	0.3664	0.1367
4	-477.904	973.807	1018.182	0.1597	0.1592	0.3999	0.1593

Finally, it can be seen that there is not much significant difference between the values of all models. All four models are valid, while Models 2 and 4 are the best-fitted to predict the fatality or non-fatality of road crashes.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Road crash data from the NH-48 rural national highway in Maharashtra, India, were studied and modeled to predict the fatality of road crashes using the negative binomial regression technique. Four models were developed incorporating variables such as the nature, time zone, and weather conditions of the crash. Two important parameters were identified under the nature of the crash, namely head-on-collision and friction. For the time zone of the crash, the two parameters (AM and PM) were identified. Five important parameters were identified under the weather conditions of the crash, namely light rain, mist/fog, heavy rain, fine, and cloudy. All four developed models were valid, while Models 2 and 4 were the best-fitted to

predict the fatality or non-fatality of road crashes. Head-on collision, AM, PM, light rain, mist/fog, heavy rain, fine, and cloudy were positively associated with the fatality of road crashes, while friction was negatively associated. The developed models can be used to predict the fatality/non-fatality of road crashes and design further road safety strategies on the highway.

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REFERENCES

- [1] "Road Accidents in India 2019," Ministry of Road Transport & Highways, India, 2019.
- [2] "Road Accidents in India 2021," Ministry of Road Transport & Highways, India, 2021.
- [3] M. Parida, S. S. Jain, and V. S. Landge, "Stochastic Modeling for Traffic Crashes on Non Urban Highways in India," presented at the Research into Practice: 22nd ARRB Conference, Canberra, Australia, 2006.
- [4] R. R. Dinu and A. Veeraragavan, "Random parameter models for accident prediction on two-lane undivided highways in India," *Journal of Safety Research*, vol. 42, no. 1, pp. 39–42, Feb. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsr.2010.11.007>.
- [5] S. S. Jain, P. K. Singh, and M. Parida, "Road Safety Audit for Four-lane National Highways," presented at the 3rd International Conference on Road Safety and Simulation - Purdue University Transportation Research Board, Indianapolis, IN, USA, 2011.
- [6] A. K. Sharma, V. S. Landge, and N. V. Deshpande, "Modeling motorcycle accident on rural highway," *International Journal of Chemical, Environmental & Biological Sciences*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 313–317, 2013.
- [7] G. Singh, S. N. Sachdeva, and M. Pal, "M5 model tree based predictive modeling of road accidents on non-urban sections of highways in India," *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, vol. 96, pp. 108–117, Nov. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2016.08.004>.
- [8] P. Vayalamkuzhi and V. Amirthalingam, "Development of Comprehensive Crash Models for Four-lane Divided Highways in Heterogeneous Traffic Condition," *Transportation Research Procedia*, vol. 17, pp. 626–635, Jan. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2016.11.117>.
- [9] G. Athipathi, S. Nagan, and T. Baskaran, "Accident Prediction on national highways in India," *International journal of theoretical and applied mechanics*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 153–165, 2017.
- [10] H. M. Naqvi and G. Tiwari, "Factors Contributing to Motorcycle Fatal Crashes on National Highways in India," *Transportation Research Procedia*, vol. 25, pp. 2084–2097, Jan. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2017.05.402>.
- [11] R. Goel, "Modelling of road traffic fatalities in India," *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, vol. 112, pp. 105–115, Mar. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2017.12.019>.
- [12] R. Bhavsar, A. Amin, and L. Zala, "Development of Model for Road Crashes and Identification of Accident Spots," *International Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems Research*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 99–111, Apr. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13177-020-00228-z>.
- [13] C. Caliendo, M. Guida, and A. Parisi, "A crash-prediction model for multilane roads," *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, vol. 39, no. 4, pp. 657–670, Jul. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2006.10.012>.
- [14] A. Montella, L. Colantuoni, and R. Lamberti, "Crash Prediction Models for Rural Motorways," *Transportation Research Record*, vol. 2083, no. 1, pp. 180–189, Jan. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.3141/2083-21>.

- [15] R. Tay, U. Barua, and L. Kattan, "Factors contributing to hit-and-run in fatal crashes," *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, vol. 41, no. 2, pp. 227–233, Mar. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2008.11.002>.
- [16] F. Chen and S. Chen, "Injury severities of truck drivers in single- and multi-vehicle accidents on rural highways," *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, vol. 43, no. 5, pp. 1677–1688, Sep. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2011.03.026>.
- [17] S. Altwajri, M. Quddus, and A. Bristow, "Analysing the Severity and Frequency of Traffic Crashes in Riyadh City Using Statistical Models," *International Journal of Transportation Science and Technology*, vol. 1, no. 4, pp. 351–364, Dec. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1260/2046-0430.1.4.351>.
- [18] Z. Li, W. Wang, P. Liu, J. M. Bigam, and D. R. Ragland, "Using Geographically Weighted Poisson Regression for county-level crash modeling in California," *Safety Science*, vol. 58, pp. 89–97, Oct. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2013.04.005>.
- [19] Y. George, T. Athanasios, and P. George, "Investigation of road accident severity per vehicle type," *Transportation Research Procedia*, vol. 25, pp. 2076–2083, Jan. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2017.05.401>.
- [20] M. Z. Hasanpour, M. R. Ahadi, A. S. Moghadam, and G. A. Behzadi, "Variable Speed Limits: Strategies to Improve Safety and Traffic Parameters for a Bottleneck," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 1535–1539, Apr. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.831>.
- [21] T. Bhowmik, S. Yasmin, and N. Eluru, "A joint econometric approach for modeling crash counts by collision type," *Analytic Methods in Accident Research*, vol. 19, pp. 16–32, Sep. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amar.2018.06.001>.
- [22] A. Valen *et al.*, "Driver-related risk factors of fatal road traffic crashes associated with alcohol or drug impairment," *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, vol. 131, pp. 191–199, Oct. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2019.06.014>.
- [23] M. Feng, X. Wang, and M. Quddus, "Developing multivariate time series models to examine the interrelations between police enforcement, traffic violations, and traffic crashes," *Analytic Methods in Accident Research*, vol. 28, Dec. 2020, Art. no. 100139, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amar.2020.100139>.
- [24] G. Fountas, A. Fonzone, N. Gharavi, and T. Rye, "The joint effect of weather and lighting conditions on injury severities of single-vehicle accidents," *Analytic Methods in Accident Research*, vol. 27, Sep. 2020, Art. no. 100124, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amar.2020.100124>.
- [25] I. J. Mrema and M. A. Dida, "A Survey of Road Accident Reporting and Driver's Behavior Awareness Systems: The Case of Tanzania," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 6009–6015, Aug. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3449>.
- [26] D. I. Tselentis, K. Folla, V. Agathangelou, and G. Yannis, "Investigating the Correlation between Driver's Characteristics and Safety Performance," *Transportation Research Procedia*, vol. 48, pp. 1254–1262, Jan. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2020.08.147>.
- [27] M. Angin and S. I. A. Ali, "Analysis of Factors Affecting Road Traffic Accidents in North Cyprus," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 7938–7943, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4547>.

Residual Strength and Crack Propagation of Reinforced Concrete Columns under High Temperatures

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ABSTRACT

In the present study, reinforced concrete columns with dimensions of 200×200×1200 mm were tested under static loading and high temperatures. In the experimental work, square cross-section columns with compressive strength of 28 MPa were tested up to failure. Mechanical properties such as compressive strength, were examined under static load and then under temperatures such as 500 and 800 °C. Column specimens with the same geometry and with concrete covers of 10 and 17 mm were also put under test. Mode of failure, ductility, stiffness, and energy dissipation for all tested specimens are discussed. The test results showed that the strength capacity of reinforced concrete columns was affected by the column cover. The increment in temperature led to a reduction in the strength-carrying capacity of the columns and increased the axial and lateral displacements. The static compressive strength was reduced by 36.84 and 48.81% when the applied temperature was 500 and 800 °C, respectively. The stiffness of the specimen with 17 mm cover was 29.27 and 46.86% less than that of 10 mm cover for axial and lateral displacement, respectively. Also, the specimen with 10 mm cover exhibited decreased energy dissipation by 1.69 and 12.54% for axial and lateral displacement.

Keywords-residual column strength; column crack propagation; reinforced concrete column; high temperature; ductility; stiffness; energy dissipation; mode of failure

I. INTRODUCTION

During the recent years, many researchers have focused on the effect of high temperature on the behavior and strength of concrete columns. When structural elements, such as the columns, are subjected to high temperatures, the strength carrying capacity and the bond are reduced. When concrete is exposed to high temperatures, this leads its resistance is decreased to 25 and 75% at 300 and 600 °C, respectively [1]. The residual strength achieved after a fire is influenced by different factors that produce concrete mechanical properties [2]. After fire exposure, concrete can recover a large proportion of its compressive strength if the temperature did not exceed 500 °C [3]. Specimens under sustained load during heating show relatively higher compressive strength compared to those that are not loaded during heating [4], due to the development of cracks under compression load that consequently slow the entry of heat through the specimen [5]. It could also be due to the presence of compression inhibiting the development of tensile cracks generated by differential expansion.

In terms of tensile strength of concrete, very little work that has been done on this area. At 400 °C, the tensile strength of concrete decreases with temperature to about 55-70% of its original value [4]. The modulus of elasticity decreases rapidly with rising temperature, depending on the aggregate type. At 400 °C, only 40-50% of the original stiffness remains. Siliceous aggregate concrete loses more stiffness than lightweight aggregate concrete [4]. Above 400 °C, the stress-strain behavior of concrete changes considerably, and it experiences a much larger degree of ductility. It has been observed that with increased temperature the strength and initial stiffness reduce and ductility increases [6]. Authors in [7] applied high temperatures on normal and high strength concrete columns with length around 3000 mm. The experimental investigation showed that high strength concrete specimens' capacities are lower than normal weight concrete's. Authors in [8] investigated the effect of axial restraint on columns under fire loads in case of fixed end specimens. The test results indicated that for specimens under the same load ratio, the axial restraint ratio has less effect on the development of column axial load. Authors in [9] investigated the load

carrying capacity of columns under fire temperature levels of 400, 600, and 900 °C for a period of exposure of 30 min at the age of 28 days. The results showed that the values of theoretical analysis are close to the ones obtained from the experimental tests. Authors in [10] declared that the strength resistance capacity of the columns decreases by 14.29, 28.57, and 42.86% at 400, 500, and 650 °C respectively. Increase in the applied temperature led to increase in the lateral and axial deflection of the tested columns. Increases in the main and tied reinforcement ratio enhance the strength capacity of the tapered column and improve ductility.

Authors in [12] utilized numerical analysis using the parametric fire model of Eurocode-1 to estimate the post-fire axial and lateral performance of reinforced concrete columns. Their study included two main steps. In the first step, the axial loadbearing capacity was evaluated from a parametric study for cantilever columns. In the second step, lateral load capacity, force-displacement behavior, stiffness, ductility, energy dissipation capacity, and residual displacements were estimated to determine the impact of fire on the behavior of the columns under lateral loads. The results showed that both the lateral load capacity and the ductility of the reinforced concrete columns decreased significantly due to fire exposure. Authors in [13] investigated the behavior and strength of Concrete Filled Steel Tube (CFST) columns under the effect of axial compression load considering parameters such as the diameter to thickness ratio and the height to diameter ratio. Strength carrying capacity and axial and lateral deformations with axial and lateral strains were explored. The test results showed that smaller heights within the same material gave higher strength capacity. The stiffness of the CFST is more than concrete and hollow steel section specimens' due to its high strength capacity with low displacement. The composite action of CFST gave more stiffness [13]. Authors in [14] simulated two columns using the finite element software SAFIR. The first was a steel profile column and the second was a Steel Profile Partially Encased in Concrete (SPPEC) column. Both columns were heated on four sides for 1 hr using the ISO 834 standard fire curve. Two boundary conditions were considered for both columns, simply and doubly supported and loaded with eccentric loading. A thermomechanical study was also carried out using the results of the thermal analysis to determine the influence of slenderness on the resistance of the steel and the partially encased profile in concrete columns under fire solicitation. The results proved that the slenderness negatively influences the fire resistance of the steel and composite columns and that the behavior of the composite columns is significantly better than that of the steel ones [14].

In this paper, the residual strength and crack propagation of prismatic reinforced concrete columns under high temperatures are investigated. The considered parameters included column cover of 10 and 17 mm and applied temperature of 500 and 800 °C, respectively.

II. EXPERIMENTAL WORK

A. Mechanical Properties of Concrete

The concrete specimens were tested for compressive strength and modulus of elasticity. The first examination was

carried out under the influence of static load until failure. Then, temperatures of 500 and 800 °C were applied. The failure load of cylindrical concrete specimens was 500.3 kN and the compressive strength was 28.31 MPa at 28 days. The splitting tensile strength with failure load of 183.3 kN was 2.59 MPa. Three different moduli of elasticity, tangent, secant, and chord, were tested under static load. Figure 1 shows the stress-strain behavior of concrete cylinders under static load.

Fig. 1. Stress-strain behavior of tested concrete cylinders.

TABLE I. STATIC MODULUS OF ELASTICITY OF CONCRETE

Mark type	Tangent	Secant	Chord
Modulus of elasticity (MPa)	27595	25565	22247

The behavior started as linear up to the inflection point. Afterward the behavior became nonlinear and the stress was not proportional with strain. The magnitude of the modulus of elasticity is shown in Table I. Based on the ACI-318, the modulus of elasticity is 25007 MPa and the compressive strength is 28.31 MPa [15].

B. Mechanical Properties under Temperature Load Test

Two groups of concrete cylinders, each consisting of three specimens, were heated under 500 and 800 °C. The temperature-time behavior of the specimens is shown in Figures 2 and 3. Figure 4 presents the stress-strain behavior of tested concrete specimens. Table II lists the modulus of elasticity values. The temperature at the cover was higher than that recorded in the core. Figure 5 shows the behavior of concrete cylinder stress-strain under static and transit dynamic load. It is clear from the behavior of concrete that its resistance to static loads is higher than its resistance to temperature. Whenever the applied temperature increases, the increase begins to strain and the curve is towards the horizontal axis, meaning that the concrete has begun to lose its resistance and stiffness decrease. Table III lists the residual strength and the reduction in compressive strength of concrete due to applied temperature loads based on static compressive strength.

TABLE II. COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH AND MODULUS OF ELASTICITY UNDER TEMPERATURE LOAD

Temperature (°C)	Compressive strength (MPa)	Secant modulus of elasticity (MPa)
500	14.49	17892
800	17.88	19874

Fig. 2. Temperature-time behavior of tested concrete cylinders at 500 °C.

Fig. 3. Temperature-time behavior of tested concrete cylinders at 800 °C.

Fig. 4. Stress-strain behavior of concrete cylinders at 500 and 800 °C.

Fig. 5. Stress-strain behavior comparison of concrete cylinders under static temperature, 500, and 800 °C.

TABLE III. RESIDUAL STRENGTH AND REDUCTION IN COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH

Applied load	Compressive strength (MPa)	% Reduction in strength	% Residual strength
Static	28.31	---	---
500 °C	17.88	36.84	63.16
800 °C	14.49	48.81	51.12

C. Specimen Details

Six specimens were tested under static and temperature load. The dimensions and geometry of the tested column were 200×200×1200 mm reinforced by 4φ12 as longitudinal reinforcement and φ6@190 mm center to center tie reinforcements as shown in Figure 6. The specimen markings are listed in Table IV. The specimen mark was based on the classification of geometry, cover, and applied load. An example follows: PC-C10-H500 in which, PC (Prismatic Specimen) is the cross section type, CXX is the Concrete cover (XX = 10 or 17 mm), and HYYY is the maximum elevated temperature (YYY = 500 or 800 °C)

TABLE IV. SPECIMEN MARKS

Specimen mark	Concrete cover (mm)	Applied temperature (°C)
PC-C10-Control	10	Static
PC-C10-H500		500 and 800
PC-C10-H800		500 and 800
PC-C17-Control	17	Static
PC-C17-H500		500 and 800
PC-C17-H800		500 and 800

Fig. 6. Specimen details.

Fig. 7. LVDT locations.

Fig. 8. Furnace chamber.

The specimens were tested under static (normal) load (the load was applied at the center of cross section and there was no eccentricity). The applied temperature load was applied from the beginning up to the specified temperature using an electric furnace designed for conducting such high-temperature experiments with dimensions of 280 mm width, 460 mm length, and 750 mm height. The heat chamber has 8 heaters with power of 1300 Watt each, therefore three phase/ 220-volt AC power was needed. The heaters were extended along the

circumference of the chamber with spacing of 100 mm along the height to ensure a uniform temperature distribution inside the chamber and around the specimen. The furnace chamber has three fixed sides and a moving one to slide the specimen inside the furnace. The furnace can take only one specimen each time. The furnace contains two type K thermocouples inside the chamber. The first thermocouple is connected to a data logger to record the real time temperature. The second one is connected to the controller of the furnace (PLC board) to control the rate of the temperature applied to the specimen. Figures 6 and 7 show the specimen geometry and dimension details. A steel cap was applied at the ends of each column to prevent stress concentration. Figure 7 presents the locations of LVDT at the center and at 200 mm above and below the center line of the specimen. Figure 8 shows the furnace chamber with the heat controller.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Behavior and Strength under Static Temperature

Every structural element, such as reinforced concrete columns, is tested first under static loading (gravity load). The control specimen was tested to ensure the strength bearing capacity and then the temperature load was applied. Axial compression load was applied to the prismatic reinforced concrete columns at the center of cross section. Figure 9 shows the loading and unloading-axial displacement of control specimens PC-C10 and PC-C17. Specimen PC-C10 gave higher strength capacity and lower axial (longitudinal) displacement because the concrete core (concrete dimensions without cover) is bigger than that of the specimen with 17 mm cover and the column is a compression member (concrete resisted compression load).

Fig. 9. Load-axial displacement of control specimens PC-C10 and PC-C17.

Figures 10 and 11 present the loading and unloading-lateral (buckling) displacement of control specimens PC-C10 and PC-C17, in which the lateral displacement was recorded 200 mm above the center line of the specimen (top), at the center of the specimen (middle), and 200 mm below the center line of the specimen (bottom). The middle displacement was the sum of the displacements from the bottom up to the center line, therefore the lateral displacement was more.

Fig. 10. Loading and unloading-lateral (buckling) displacement of PC-C10.

Fig. 11. Loading and unloading-lateral (buckling) displacement of PC-C17.

Specimen PC-C10 gave higher strength capacity and lower lateral displacement than PC-C17 due to the cover. The increase in the concrete cover reduces the load resistance of the column to lateral displacement (buckling) due to the reduction in concrete stiffness. Table V lists the maximum and failure loads with corresponding axial and lateral displacements for the control specimens PC-C10 and PC-C17 static temperature. Figure 12 shows the comparison between the control specimens with 10 and 17 mm cover. Increase in cover width lead to reduction in strength carrying capacity by 13% and increased lateral displacement by 23.05% and 63.72%.

Fig. 12. Middle lateral displacement of PC-C10 and PC-C17.

TABLE V. MAXIMUM AND FAILURE LOADS WITH CORRESPONDING AXIAL AND LATERAL DISPLACEMENTS

Specimen	Maximum load P_m and failure load P_f (kN)		Axial displacement at P_m and P_f (mm)		Lateral displacement at P_m and P_f (mm)		
	P_m	P_f	Δ_m	Δ_f	$\delta_{Bm} (\delta_{Bf})$	$\delta_{Mm} (\delta_{Mf})$	$\delta_{Tm} (\delta_{Tf})$
PC-C10 Control	1100	1050	16.53	17.00	2.01 (2.15)	2.26 (3.24)	2.02 (2.19)
PC-C17 Control	958	897	20.34	21.25	2.43 (2.58)	3.70 (3.82)	2.48 (2.62)

B. Behavior and Strength under Elevated Temperatures

Two different temperatures, 500 and 800 °C, were applied. The tested specimens had the same geometry with the control specimens. The temperature was applied with a rate of 10 °C/min up to the designed final value. Figures 13 and 14 show the behavior of specimens PC-C10 and PC-C17. Table VI lists the strength capacity of each specimen with corresponding axial and lateral displacements.

Fig. 13. Comparison between heated and unheated specimens with 10 mm cover.

Fig. 14. Comparison between heated and unheated specimens with 17 mm cover.

TABLE VI. MAXIMUM AND FAILURE LOADS WITH CORRESPONDING AXIAL AND LATERAL DISPLACEMENTS

Specimen	Maximum load P_{mh} (kN)	Axial displacement at P_{mh} and P_f (mm)	Lateral displacement at P_{mh} and P_f (mm)		
	P_{mh}	Δ_{mh}	δ_{Bmh}	δ_{Mmh}	δ_{Tmh}
PC-C10-H500	590	12.75	0.5	1.32	1.6
PC-C10-H800	385	12.29	4.39	6.93	5.59
PC-C17-H500	385	18.50	1.63	1.85	2.66
PC-C17-H800	370	15.90	2.31	4.03	3.98

C. Stiffness of the Tested Specimens

The obtained load-displacement (axial and lateral) curves were acquired from the recorded measurements at mid, top, and bottom of the central mid height of each specimen (300 mm away from the mid height for each specimen). In the static tests, the applied axial normal load was applied at the bottom cross section center. Stiffness is the resistance of an elastic body to displacement or deformation by an applied force. The stiffness is defined as the ratio of the ultimate load to ultimate load displacement (axial and lateral). Table VII lists the calculated stiffness values of each specimen.

TABLE VII. AXIAL AND LATERAL STIFFNESS UNDER STATIC TEMPERATURE

Specimen	Stiffness-axial displacement k_a (kN/mm)	Stiffness-lateral-middle-displacement k_l (kN/mm)
PC-C10-Control	66.55	486.73
PC-C17-Control	47.10	258.65

D. Ductility of the Tested Specimens

Ductility is the ability of a concrete member, such as a reinforced concrete column, to bear or endure considerable displacements before failure. The ductility of concrete column is very important because it provides signs of collapse or failure. Concrete is a brittle material, i.e. it fails within the plastic zone (no elastic-plastic zone). The ductility for all tested specimens was calculated by dividing the displacement (axial and lateral) at ultimate load by the displacement at yield. Table VIII shows the results.

TABLE VIII. AXIAL AND LATERAL DUCTILITY OF TESTED SPECIMENS UNDER STATIC LOADINGS

Specimen	Ductility (axial)	Ductility (lateral)
PC-C10-Control	1.04	1.43
PC-C17-Control	1.04	1.03

E. Energy Absorption of the Tested Specimens

The energy absorption is the area under the load-(longitudinal and lateral) displacement curve. The resistance of plain concrete against applied load is less due to the low energy dissipation and low resistance in tensile strength. The energy absorption can be considered for the evaluation of the post-cracking behavior of reinforced concrete columns. Table IX lists the energy dissipation values of the tested specimens.

TABLE IX. ENERGY DISSIPATION UNDER STATIC TEMPERATURE

Specimen	Energy dissipation (axial) (kN.mm)	Energy dissipation (lateral)-middle (kN.mm)
PC-C10-Control	3613	3975
PC-C17-Control	3675	4545

F. Mode of Failure

Figure 15 shows the crack propagation under static and temperature loads as 500 and 800 °C. The final failure that occurred in the concrete columns under static load was flexural. When elevated temperature was applied, the intensity of the cracks increased.

Fig. 15. Crack propagation: (a) Control specimen-static test, (b) PC-C10-H500, (c) PC-C17-H500, (d) PC-C10-H800, and (e) PC-C17-H800.

G. Discussion

The experimental tests on reinforced concrete columns under static and temperature loads showed that the increased concrete cover leads to reduced strength capacity of concrete columns because the concrete core becomes smaller. When the reinforced concrete column specimens are exposed to elevated temperatures, the chemical composition and physical structure of concrete change considerably, so its compressive strength reduces. Table X lists the comparison between the two control specimens PC-C10 and PC-C17, with PC-C10 being used as the reference. The stiffness of specimen PC-C17 was less than that of PC-C10 because the strength capacity was more and the displacement less due to the moment of inertia of core concrete column in the case of 10 mm cover that lead increased elasticity. When the energy dissipation becomes less, the applied load will be absorbed by the column which works as full support and the other structural elements in the building become safer.

TABLE X. COMPARISON BETWEEN CONTROL SPECIMENS UNDER STATIC TEMPERATURE

Specimen	Decrease in stiffness (%)		Decrease in energy dissipation (%)	
	Axial	Lateral	Axial	Lateral
PC-C10-Control	---	---	1.69	12.54
PC-C17-Control	29.27	46.86	---	---

Regarding specimens under temperature load, the applied service gravity load was 35% of the ultimate strength capacity. The increase in the applied temperature lead to a decrease of elasticity, the column stiffness became less, and therefore the strength carrying capacity reduced with rising temperature. As mentioned in Table VI, the strength carrying capacity of PC-C10-H800 was less by 34.75% than the one of PC-C10-H500. A decrease 3.9% was recorded for the cover of 17 mm in comparison with 10 mm. Increase in applied temperature reduced the compressive strength and the resistance of the column was reduced, reflecting on the strength carrying capacity. The crack propagation and intensity increased for applied temperature load of 800 °C when compared with static and 500 °C temperature loads. The cracks had a wider distribution in the case of 10 mm cover as compare to specimens with 17 mm cover.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The contribution of the current study lies in the knowledge of the structural behavior of the columns, the extent to which it is affected by high temperatures, and the damages resulting from thermal load on the mechanical properties and the bearing capacity. Based on the test results and observations about the reduction in concrete compressive strength due to applied temperature of 500 and 800°C, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The strength carrying capacity of the tested columns decreased when they were subjected to high temperatures and the residual strength increased when the applied temperature increased.
- Axial and lateral displacements increased due to the applied temperature.
- Concrete cover plays an important role in reducing the effect of temperature. The cracks do not reach the reinforcement at specific temperatures.
- Greater number and size of the cracks that developed due to the applied temperature were observed when the cracks appeared in the early stages of applied heating. Crushing that occurred in the concrete and lateral displacements (buckling) were predominant failure modes under at the applied temperatures.
- The present study gave results for the residual resistance of reinforced concrete columns exposed to high temperatures through which a decision can be given whether it is suitable to keep this structural element or not in the building. Knowing the aging of cracks in relation to temperature helps making structural decisions. The decision to maintain the reinforced concrete columns can be based on knowing and comparing their mechanical properties and behavior under the influence of high temperature.

REFERENCES

- [1] *TR 33 Assessment and repair of fire-damaged concrete structures*. UK: Concrete Society, 1990.
- [2] B. Chen, C. Li, and L. Chen, "Experimental study of mechanical properties of normal-strength concrete exposed to high temperatures at an early age," *Fire Safety Journal*, vol. 44, no. 7, pp. 997–1002, Oct. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.firesaf.2009.06.007>.
- [3] B. L. Williams, "Fire performance of FRP-strengthened reinforced concrete flexural members.," Ph.D. dissertation, Queen's University, Kingston, Canada, 2004.
- [4] U. Schneider, "Concrete at high temperatures — A general review," *Fire Safety Journal*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 55–68, Apr. 1988, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0379-7112\(88\)90033-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0379-7112(88)90033-1).
- [5] G. A. Khoury, "Effect of fire on concrete and concrete structures," *Progress in Structural Engineering and Materials*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 429–447, 2000, <https://doi.org/10.1002/pse.51>.
- [6] U. Schneider, "Modelling of concrete behaviour at high temperatures," in *Design of structures against fire*, 1986, pp. 53–69.
- [7] V. K. R. Kodur, F.-P. Cheng, T.-C. Wang, and M. A. Sultan, "Effect of Strength and Fiber Reinforcement on Fire Resistance of High-Strength Concrete Columns," *Journal of Structural Engineering*, vol. 129, no. 2, pp. 253–259, Feb. 2003, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9445\(2003\)129:2\(253\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9445(2003)129:2(253)).
- [8] B. O. Wu and Y. H. Li, "Experimental research on fire performance of axially restrained RC columns with L-shaped cross section," in *Proceedings of the Fifth International Conference on Structures in Fire*, 2008, pp. 451–462.
- [9] H. K. Alaa, "Structural Behavior of Eccentrically Loaded Reinforced Concrete Columns Exposed to Fire Flame," Ph.D. dissertation, Mustansiriyah University, Baghdad, Iraq, 2019.
- [10] F. Al-Naqeeb and H. Al-Thairy, "The behavior of reinforced concrete columns exposure to eccentric loads at high temperature," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 1895, no. 1, Feb. 2021, Art. no. 012055, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1895/1/012055>.
- [11] H. N. G. Al-Maliki, A. J. H. Alshimmeri, A. M. Ali, Y. M. Madhloom, and Y. Gamli, "Nonlinear Simulation Analysis of Tapered Reinforced Concrete Column (solid and Hollow) Behavior Under Axial Load," *International Journal of GEOMATE*, vol. 21, no. 86, pp. 131–146, 2019.
- [12] M. Baghdadi, M. S. Dimia, and D. Baghdadi, "A Parametric Study of Fire-Damaged Reinforced Concrete Columns under Lateral Loads," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 9113–9119, Oct. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5172>.
- [13] A. N. Hassooni and S. R. A. Zaidee, "Behavior and Strength of Composite Columns under the Impact of Uniaxial Compression

- Loading," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 8843–8849, Aug. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4753>.
- [14] F. Boursas, R. Boufarh, and B. Maghaghi, "The Influence of Slenderness in Steel and Composite Columns under Fire Conditions," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 10145–10150, Feb. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5560>.
- [15] *ACI Committee 318, ACI CODE-318-19(22): Building Code Requirements for Structural Concrete and Commentary (Reapproved 2022)*. ACI, 2020.

Evaluation of Aircraft Emissions at Bucharest Henri Coanda Airport

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ABSTRACT

This study presents the influence of aircraft movements on air quality by highlighting the contribution of landings and/or takeoffs at Henri Coanda Airport, Bucharest. An experimental campaign was carried out using a mobile laboratory equipped with reference instruments for the main air pollutants (NO, NO₂, NO_x, SO₂, CO, and O₃) and a meteorological station to measure wind speed and direction, air temperature, pressure, and relative humidity at a height of 10 m above the ground. The mobile testing laboratory was located inside the airport near the passenger embarking area, and measurements were carried out for 7 days. Air sampling was carried out at a height of 3.5 m above the ground. Pollutant levels were continuously measured throughout the measurement period, with high-precision equipment and a 10-second interval. The results obtained showed an increase in pollutant concentrations during takeoffs and/or landings, providing an initial assessment of gaseous pollutant levels and hourly distribution. Airport authorities can use this assessment to balance aircraft and passenger movements to minimize human exposure to gaseous pollutants. Furthermore, this study used the Pearson correlation between each pollutant and meteorological parameters to establish the best conditions for passengers to be present on the airport premises. The results showed that wind speed and direction directly influence the distribution of gaseous pollutants, especially during landings and takeoffs.

Keywords-emissions;airport; pollutants; wind; correlation; Romania

I. INTRODUCTION

With the rapid increase in air traffic, aircraft emissions have attracted widespread attention as an important source of air pollution [1]. Aircraft emissions originate from the fuel burned in the aircraft engines. Aircraft gas turbine engines, which like many other vehicle engines, produce nitrogen oxides, hydrocarbons, carbon dioxide, water vapor, sulfur oxides, particulates, and other trace compounds. Carbon monoxide is formed as a result of incomplete combustion of the carbon in fuel. Nitrogen oxides (NO and NO₂) are produced when fuel is burned at high temperatures, as in the combustion process [2]. In [3-10], the mechanisms for gaseous pollutant formations and emissions are described by analyzing the main components: hydrocarbons, carbon dioxide, sulfur, nitrogen oxides, and particulate matter. Most of these studies also evaluated the influence of gaseous pollutants on human and environmental

health. The impact of commercial aviation emissions on air quality has been estimated to be responsible for approximately 16,000 premature deaths each year around the world [11]. In [12], important research questions on aviation-attributable air pollution were highlighted, such as global vs. local impacts, aviation impact in a changing atmosphere, and emission reduction strategies focused on technological changes such as alternative jet fuels [13-16]. In [17], the sources and contributions of submicron particles (PM) were identified at the UK's second-largest airport to provide information on whether and under what circumstances ultrafine particles (UFP) might be correlated with noise exposure and, therefore, might need to be taken into consideration in studies investigating associations between aircraft noise and health outcomes. In [18-19], pollutant gas emissions including NO_x, hydrocarbons (HC), and CO from aircraft during landing and take-off (LTO) cycles were estimated for 2010 at Kayseri Airport, Turkey. In [20],

the impact of aircraft on air quality was investigated, focusing on aviation-attributable PM_{2.5} on scales ranging from local (a few km) to continental (hundreds of km) using the Community Multiscale Air Quality-Advanced Plume Treatment (CMAQ-APT) model for US airports. In [21], ultrafine particles (UFP) were monitored at Heathrow Airport in the autumn of 2017, collecting high-resolution data from NO_x, PM, and black carbon analyzers on site. In [22-23] the impact of the airport on the environment was investigated, due to the proximity of the airport to the historic city of Venice and the fragile ecosystem of the lagoon surrounding the city. In [24], the NO_x emissions from commercial short-haul flights were assessed and quantified based on numerous actual flights, actual emissions, and actual meteorological data. In [25], the impact of Beirut Airport activities on local air quality emissions of NO₂ and VOCs was investigated, including emissions from aircraft LTO operations, ground support equipment, stationary sources, and airside and landside vehicles. This study, which was the first comprehensive emission inventory in the Middle East region, provided a method to assess airport emissions in a country without data. In [26], a systematic review of the impact of commercial aircraft activity on air quality near airports was presented. In [28], an airport-specific green rating framework was presented as a tool to assess the greenery of airport operations based on environmental indicators.

The current study investigated the formation and distribution of gaseous pollutants within the Henri Coanda Airport, Bucharest, focusing on the passenger embarkation area, which is closely related to the measures that are nowadays enforced in Europe called "decarbonizing airports". This study is the first of its kind at that airport, and investigates the causal relationship between meteorological parameters, especially wind speed and direction, and gaseous pollutant concentrations and aircraft movements.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Henri Coanda International Airport Issues

The Henri Coanda International Airport is the only one in service for Romania's capital, Bucharest, located 15 km north of the city, as shown in Figure 1, and has an area of 605 hectares.

Fig. 1. Henri Coanda International Airport location. Image from Google Earth. © Airbus SNES/ Airbus, Maxar Technologies.

Figure 2 presents statistics related to the passenger numbers and aircraft movements within the airport [29].

Fig. 2. Henri Coanda International Airport: (a) Passenger traffic and (b) aircraft movements.

Passenger and aircraft movements at Henri Coanda International Airport were constantly increasing until 2019, and now, after a period of low activity due to the SarsCov-2 pandemic, this trend is resuming at a higher rate, but not reaching the 2019 values. The increase in movements between 2016 and 2015 was 11.36% for aircraft and 18.38% for passengers, while the increase in movements between 2021 and 2022 was 41.5% for aircraft and 82.2% for passengers. The constant increase in airport aircraft movements may cause air quality problems. The national measurement and assessment stations are quite far from the airport, and thus their data do not show the reality within its premises. Therefore, no data are available on gaseous pollutants within the airport.

B. Experimental Campaign

Figure 3 shows the monitoring systems for air pollutants and weather for meteorological parameters placed in a mobile laboratory, belonging to the Romanian Research and Development Institute for Gas Turbines COMOTI, Bucharest. The mobile laboratory combined reference instruments for the major air pollutants (HORIBA AP360 series, CO, SO_x, NO_x, and O₃) and a meteorological station to measure wind speed and direction, air temperature, pressure, and relative humidity at 10 m above ground. The mobile testing laboratory was located about 240 m off the runway and Figure 4 shows its location in the airport area. Polluted air sampling was carried out at a height of 3.5 m from the ground. The pollutants were continuously measured, with 10 s intervals, throughout the entire measurement period with high-precision equipment:

- NO, NO₂, and NO_x were measured with a Horiba APNA 360 using chemoluminescence (reference method: SREN 14211:2012).
- SO₂ was measured with Horiba APSA 360, using UV fluorescence (reference method: SREN 14212:2012).

- O₃ was measured with Horiba APOA 360, using UV photometry (reference method: SREN 14625:2012).
- CO was measured with Horiba APMA 360, using nondispersive infrared (NDIR, reference method SREN 14626:2012).

Fig. 3. The monitoring system of air pollutants.

Fig. 4. Location of the mobile laboratory on the runway. Image from Google Earth. © Airbus SNES/ Airbus, Maxar Technologies.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data recorded by the mobile laboratory for 7 days were NO₂, CO, SO₂, and O₃, and their variation versus wind speed and direction was drawn to correlate with each other. The

aircraft types were A320, A319, A318, B737, ATR72, ATR42, and others, including helicopters, small airplanes, military airplanes, etc. "Others" represented 25% of the total aircraft LTOs during the 7-day monitoring period. Day 1 of movement monitoring was Tuesday. Day 7 had the most movements, so the other 6 days are represented as a percentage of it as follows: Day 1: 99.7%, Day 2: 99.7%, Day 3: 96.76%, Day 4: 96.3%, Day 5: 70.83%, and Day 6: 81.94%. Figures 5-11 show the evolution of gaseous pollutants for the 7 days of monitoring and the number of classified aircraft for an assessment of their contribution to overall pollution during landings and take-offs.

For Day 1, the mean measurements were NO₂ = 17.95 µg/m³, CO = 0.24 mg/m³, SO₂ = 1.58 µg/m³, O₃ = 36.30 µg/m³, WS = 5.17 m/s, and WD = 15.86°. As shown in Figure 5, some CO₂, SO₂, and CO-related peaks appear during the first hours of the day due to landing activity and wind speed and direction. Higher concentrations of NO₂, CO, and SO₂ appear between 17:00 and 18:00 due to increased LTOs within that interval. Within 01:00-06:00, there were no take-offs and only one landing, therefore, only one peak was registered.

For Day 2, the mean measurements were NO₂ = 16.30 µg/m³, CO = 0.25 mg/m³, SO₂ = 1 µg/m³, O₃ = 36.46 µg/m³, WS = 5.12 m/s, and WD = 25.54°. As shown in Figure 6, as the wind speed and direction changed, the registered values drastically decreased, even though between 21:00-22:00 there were many take-offs. Between 05:00 and 08:00, wind speed and direction changed, and although there were fewer movements, some peaks were registered.

For Day 3, the mean measurements were NO₂ = 23.43 µg/m³, CO = 0.27 mg/m³, SO₂ = 1.01 µg/m³, O₃ = 19.65 µg/m³, WS = 2.01 m/s, and WD = 143.29°. Figure 7 shows that in the first hours of monitoring, several peaks were registered and along with the change in wind speed and direction, the concentration tendency was increased. Around 08:00, the peaks increased due to the larger movements and settlement of the wind to almost atmospheric calm. Around 13:00, other peaks were registered due to LTOs, but larger peaks appeared during 16:00-17:00 due to the same activity but also the change in wind speed and direction. This day was one of the busiest on the airport in terms of LTOs.

Fig. 5. Evolution of SO₂, CO, O₃, and NO₂ concentrations vs. wind speed for Day 1.

Fig. 6. Evolution of SO₂, CO, O₃, and NO₂ concentrations vs. wind speed for Day 2.

Fig. 7. Evolution of SO₂, CO, O₃, and NO₂ concentrations vs. wind speed for Day 3.

Fig. 8. Evolution of SO₂, CO, O₃, and NO₂ concentrations vs. wind speed for Day 4.

Fig. 9. Evolution of SO₂, CO, O₃, and NO₂ concentrations vs. wind speed for Day 5.

Fig. 10. Evolution of SO₂, CO, O₃, and NO₂ concentrations vs. wind speed for Day 6.

Fig. 11. Evolution of SO₂, CO, O₃, and NO₂ concentrations vs. wind speed for Day 7.

For Day 4, the mean values were $NO_2 = 25.63 \mu g/m^3$, $CO = 0.4 mg/m^3$, $SO_2 = 2.01 \mu g/m^3$, $O_3 = 19.81 \mu g/m^3$, $WS = 3.26 m/s$, and $WD = 97.08^\circ$. Day 4 had the lowest activity, so only a few small peaks were registered during the first hours, as shown in Figure 8. A bundle of peaks was recorded around 11:00 when the wind speed dropped, although the movements were low. Around 15:00, the number of movements increased and the wind speed was at its lowest, so the peaks are well represented.

For Day 5, the mean values were $NO_2 = 22.31 \mu g/m^3$, $CO = 0.28 mg/m^3$, $SO_2 = 1.82 \mu g/m^3$, $O_3 = 34.42 \mu g/m^3$, $WS = 2.55 m/s$, and $WD = 106.38^\circ$. Landings in the first hours had a minimal impact on the pollution values both because there were few and the wind speed and direction spread the pollutants. Around 09:00 a small peak appeared due to the large number of takeoffs but again wind speed and direction played a role in spreading the pollutants. After 10:00, the wind changed direction and its speed dropped. Therefore, peaks appeared and concentrations increased. Between 14:00 and 15:00, peaks appeared due to the constant large number of landing/takeoffs.

For Day 6, the mean measured values were $NO_2 = 15.27 \mu g/m^3$, $CO = 0.23 mg/m^3$, $SO_2 = 0.96 \mu g/m^3$, $O_3 = 44.21 \mu g/m^3$, $WS = 4.83 m/s$, and $WD = 26.73^\circ$. As in the previous days, some peaks appeared during LTOs at midnight, and then, until 07:00, the concentrations did not vary anymore. In the interval 08:00-09:00, due to the relatively many LTOs and changes in wind speed and direction, some peaks appeared. Additionally, high pollutant concentrations appeared after 14:00 and were kept relatively high until 22:00.

For Day 7, the mean values measured were: $NO_2 = 13.79 \mu g/m^3$, $CO = 0.23 mg/m^3$, $SO_2 = 0.4 \mu g/m^3$, $O_3 = 33.67 \mu g/m^3$, $WS = 5.79 m/s$, and $WD = 16.69^\circ$. This day is characterized by the most aircraft movements, but the overall trend was similar to the previous 6 days. Thus, some peaks appeared during LTOs at midnight, and then, until 07:00, the concentrations did not vary anymore. In the interval 08:00-09:00, some peaks appeared due to the relatively many LTOs and the changes in wind speed and direction. In addition, high pollutant concentrations appeared after 14:00 and remained relatively high until 22:00.

Pearson correlation was used to investigate the relationship between the pollutant concentrations and wind speed and direction. The Pearson correlation coefficient is used to measure the strength of a linear association between two variables, where the value $r = 1$ means a perfect positive correlation and the value $r = -1$ means a perfect negative correlation. Table I shows the Pearson correlations between NO_2 , CO , SO_2 , and O_3 concentrations, and wind speed and direction. Table I shows the strong positive correlation between the gaseous pollutant concentrations, except O_3 which shows a negative correlation, and wind speed and direction.

For Day 1, the correlation with wind speed is positive for NO_2 , CO , and SO_2 , but negative for O_3 , while the correlation with wind direction is almost null for NO_2 and SO_2 , positive for CO , and strongly positive for O_3 . For Day 2, the correlation with wind speed was negative for NO_2 , almost null for CO , and

positive for O_3 , while the correlation with wind direction was almost null for CO and SO_2 , positive for NO_2 , and strongly negative for O_3 . For Day 3, the correlation with wind speed is positive for SO_2 and O_3 and almost null for CO and NO_2 , while the correlation with wind direction is strongly positive for NO_2 and CO , strongly negative for O_3 , and almost null for SO_2 .

For Day 4, the correlation with wind speed is negative for NO_2 , almost null for CO , positive for SO_2 , and strongly positive (0.9) for O_3 , while the correlation with wind direction is almost null for CO , strongly positive for NO_2 , strongly negative for SO_2 , and very strongly negative for O_3 . For Day 5, the correlation of wind speed was strongly negative with NO_2 and SO_2 and almost null with CO , while the correlation of wind direction was almost null with NO_2 and CO and weakly negative for SO_2 and O_3 . For Day 6, the correlation of wind speed was almost null with NO_2 , strongly positive with SO_2 and O_3 , and strongly negative with CO , while the correlation of wind direction was almost null with NO_2 and O_3 , negative with SO_2 , and positive with CO . For Day 7, the correlation of wind speed was negative with NO_2 , SO_2 , and CO and strongly positive with O_3 , while the correlation of wind direction was strongly positive with O_3 and negative with NO_2 , CO , and SO_2 .

TABLE I. CORRELATIONS OF NO_2 , CO , SO_2 , AND O_3 WITH WIND SPEED AND WIND DIRECTION

	Day 1				Day 2			
	NO_2	CO	SO_2	O_3	NO_2	CO	SO_2	O_3
NO_2	1				1			
CO	0.63	1			0.78	1		
SO_2	0.76	0.60	1		0.83	0.84	1	
O_3	-0.75	-0.38	-0.59	1	-0.26	0.21	0.11	1
WS	0.26	0.15	0.22	-0.21	-0.15	0.03	0.12	0.66
WD	-0.10	-0.15	-0.07	0.27	0.13	-0.01	-0.05	-0.31
	Day 3				Day 4			
	NO_2	CO	SO_2	O_3	NO_2	CO	SO_2	O_3
NO_2	1				1			
CO	0.73	1			0.72	1		
SO_2	0.73	0.42	1		0.48	0.28	1	
O_3	-0.76	-0.58	-0.47	1	-0.32	-0.05	0.44	1
WS	-0.09	-0.04	0.18	0.27	-0.35	-0.08	0.31	0.90
WD	0.40	0.48	0.07	-0.42	0.22	-0.02	-0.29	-0.73
	Day 5				Day 6			
	NO_2	CO	SO_2	O_3	NO_2	CO	SO_2	O_3
NO_2	1				1			
CO	0.38	1			0.32	1		
SO_2	0.70	-0.03	1		0.45	-0.17	1	
O_3	-0.26	-0.41	0.36	1	-0.16	-0.44	0.14	1
WS	-0.32	0.02	-0.47	-0.14	0.02	-0.61	0.45	0.42
WD	0.03	0.05	-0.12	-0.16	-0.05	0.17	-0.21	0.09
	Day 7							
	NO_2	CO	SO_2	O_3				
NO_2	1							
CO	0.65	1						
SO_2	0.84	0.55	1					
O_3	-0.47	-0.30	-0.40	1				
WS	-0.31	-0.18	-0.36	0.43				
WD	-0.17	-0.15	-0.30	0.33				

Tables II and III show the percentages for each aircraft type for all days of monitoring for takeoffs and landings, respectively.

TABLE II. TAKEOFF AIRCRAFT TYPE PERCENTAGES

Day	Takeoff Aircraft types						
	A320	A319	A318	B737	ATR72	ATR42	Other
1	12.50	5.77	11.54	28.85	1.92	16.35	23.08
2	12.15	6.54	9.35	28.97	2.80	15.89	24.30
3	10.38	8.49	6.60	30.19	3.77	14.15	26.42
4	13.59	6.80	6.80	28.16	5.83	10.68	28.16
5	16.88	7.79	10.39	31.17	3.90	7.79	22.08
6	10.00	13.33	7.78	32.22	3.33	12.22	21.11
7	11.32	8.49	9.43	30.19	2.83	15.09	22.64

TABLE III. LANDING AIRCRAFT TYPE PERCENTAGES

Day	Landing Aircraft types						
	A320	A319	A318	B737	ATR72	ATR42	Other
1	10.91	6.36	10.00	28.18	1.82	17.27	25.45
2	13.08	7.48	11.21	28.97	2.80	12.15	24.30
3	9.71	6.80	6.80	32.04	3.88	15.53	25.24
4	14.29	6.67	6.67	26.67	5.71	13.33	28.16
5	14.47	10.53	7.89	32.89	3.95	6.58	23.68
6	10.34	12.64	10.34	31.03	3.45	10.34	21.84
7	12.73	7.27	8.18	29.09	2.73	15.45	24.55

IV. CONCLUSIONS

- The peaks for pollutant concentrations appeared during the period of a high number of LTOs, within a relatively short time, and with a direct correlation between the number of movements and concentration values.
- It is very difficult to determine a direct correlation between aircraft type and pollutant concentrations because of the number of different aircraft types that land or take off in a short time.
- Wind speed and direction directly influence pollutant concentration values since wind is the most important agent involved in pollutants' dispersion.
- Wind speed influences pollutant concentrations and wind direction influences their movement.
- Pearson's correlation is a very useful tool in assessing the direct correlation between meteorological parameters and gaseous pollutant concentrations.
- Lower pollutant concentration values were recorded on days with high wind speed (days, 1, 2, 6, and 7), while higher pollutant concentrations were recorded on days 3, 4, and 5 when the wind speed was lower.
- On days when the wind direction was toward the mobile lab, the pollutant concentrations were higher (Days 3, 4, and 5).
- On Days 1, 2, 6, and 7, when the wind direction was away from the mobile laboratory, the pollutant concentration values were lower.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Masiol and R. M. Harrison, "Quantification of air quality impacts of London Heathrow Airport (UK) from 2005 to 2012," *Atmospheric Environment*, vol. 116, pp. 308–319, Sep. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2015.06.048>.
- [2] G. Stratmann *et al.*, "NO and NO_y in the upper troposphere: Nine years of CARIBIC measurements onboard a passenger aircraft," *Atmospheric Environment*, vol. 133, pp. 93–111, May 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2016.02.035>.
- [3] N. Harkat, A. Rahmane, and I. Bendjemila, "The Impact of Industrial Air Pollution on the Urban Environment of Setif: Modeling and Mapping of Total Suspended Particles," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 9431–9439, Dec. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5256>.
- [4] J. Rissman, S. Arunachalam, M. Woody, J. J. West, T. BenDor, and F. S. Binkowski, "A plume-in-grid approach to characterize air quality impacts of aircraft emissions at the Hartsfield–Jackson Atlanta International Airport," *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, vol. 13, no. 18, pp. 9285–9302, Sep. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-13-9285-2013>.
- [5] N. Hudda and S. A. Fruin, "International Airport Impacts to Air Quality: Size and Related Properties of Large Increases in Ultrafine Particle Number Concentrations," *Environmental Science & Technology*, vol. 50, no. 7, pp. 3362–3370, Apr. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.5b05313>.
- [6] K. H. Jung, F. Artigas, and J. Y. Shin, "Personal, indoor, and outdoor exposure to VOCs in the immediate vicinity of a local airport," *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, vol. 173, no. 1, pp. 555–567, Feb. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-010-1404-9>.
- [7] A. A. Siyal, S. R. Samo, Z. A. Siyal, K. C. Mukwana, S. A. Jiskani, and A. Mengal, "Assessment of Air Pollution by PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} in Nawabshah City, Sindh, Pakistan," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 3757–3761, Feb. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2440>.
- [8] S. H. L. Yim, M. E. J. Stettler, and S. R. H. Barrett, "Air quality and public health impacts of UK airports. Part II: Impacts and policy assessment," *Atmospheric Environment*, vol. 67, pp. 184–192, Mar. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2012.10.017>.
- [9] D. A. Pamplona and C. J. P. Alves, "Civil Aircraft Emissions Study and Pollutant Forecasting at a Brazilian Airport," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 5217–5220, Feb. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3227>.
- [10] A. Mahashabde *et al.*, "Assessing the environmental impacts of aircraft noise and emissions," *Progress in Aerospace Sciences*, vol. 47, no. 1, pp. 15–52, Jan. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paerosci.2010.04.003>.
- [11] C. Grobler *et al.*, "Marginal climate and air quality costs of aviation emissions," *Environmental Research Letters*, vol. 14, no. 11, Aug. 2019, Art. no. 114031, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ab4942>.
- [12] I. C. Dedoussi, "Implications of future atmospheric composition in decision-making for sustainable aviation," *Environmental Research Letters*, vol. 16, no. 3, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/abe74d>.
- [13] C. A. Arter, J. J. Buonocore, C. Moniruzzaman, D. Yang, J. Huang, and S. Arunachalam, "Air quality and health-related impacts of traditional and alternate jet fuels from airport aircraft operations in the U.S.," *Environment International*, vol. 158, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 106958, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2021.106958>.
- [14] G. Cican, D. E. Crunteanu, R. Mirea, L. C. Ceatra, and C. Leventiu, "Biodiesel from Recycled Sunflower and Palm Oil—A Sustainable Fuel for Microturbo-Engines Used in Airside Applications," *Sustainability*, vol. 15, no. 3, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15032079>.
- [15] G. Cican, M. Deaconu, R. Mirea, L. C. Ceatra, and M. Cretu, "An Experimental Investigation to Use the Biodiesel Resulting from Recycled Sunflower Oil, and Sunflower Oil with Palm Oil as Fuels for Aviation Turbo-Engines," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 18, no. 10, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18105189>.
- [16] G. Cican, A. Toma, C. Pușcașu, and R. Catana, "Jet CAT P80 Thermal Analyses and Performance Assessment Using Different Fuels Types," *Journal of Thermal Science*, vol. 27, no. 4, pp. 389–393, Aug. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11630-018-1026-z>.
- [17] A. H. Tremper *et al.*, "Sources of particle number concentration and noise near London Gatwick Airport," *Environment International*, vol. 161, Mar. 2022, Art. no. 107092, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2022.107092>.

- [18] J. Ramakrishnan, T. Liu, R. Yu, K. Seshadri, and Z. Gou, "Towards greener airports: Development of an assessment framework by leveraging sustainability reports and rating tools," *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, vol. 93, Mar. 2022, Art. no. 106740, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2022.106740>.
- [19] İ. Yılmaz, "Emissions from passenger aircraft at Kayseri Airport, Turkey," *Journal of Air Transport Management*, vol. 58, pp. 176–182, Jan. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jairtraman.2016.11.001>.
- [20] M. C. Woody, H. W. Wong, J. J. West, and S. Arunachalam, "Multiscale predictions of aviation-attributable PM_{2.5} for U.S. airports modeled using CMAQ with plume-in-grid and an aircraft-specific 1-D emission model," *Atmospheric Environment*, vol. 147, pp. 384–394, Dec. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2016.10.016>.
- [21] B. Stacey, R. M. Harrison, and F. D. Pope, "Evaluation of aircraft emissions at London Heathrow Airport," *Atmospheric Environment*, vol. 254, Jun. 2021, Art. no. 118226, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2021.118226>.
- [22] E. Innocente, E. Pecorari, D. Zannoni, and G. Rampazzo, "Methodology choice could affect air quality interpretation? A case study for an international airport, Marco Polo, Venice," *Science of The Total Environment*, vol. 707, Mar. 2020, Art. no. 135326, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.135326>.
- [23] C. Zhang *et al.*, "Mitigation effects of alternative aviation fuels on non-volatile particulate matter emissions from aircraft gas turbine engines: A review," *Science of The Total Environment*, vol. 820, May 2022, Art. no. 153233, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.153233>.
- [24] E. T. Turgut and O. Usanmaz, "An assessment of cruise NO_x emissions of short-haul commercial flights," *Atmospheric Environment*, vol. 171, pp. 191–204, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2017.10.013>.
- [25] T. Mokalled *et al.*, "Identifying the impact of Beirut Airport's activities on local air quality - Part I: Emissions inventory of NO₂ and VOCs," *Atmospheric Environment*, vol. 187, pp. 435–444, Aug. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2018.04.036>.
- [26] K. Riley, R. Cook, E. Carr, and B. Manning, "A systematic review of the impact of commercial aircraft activity on air quality near airports," *City and Environment Interactions*, vol. 11, Aug. 2021, Art. no. 100066, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cacint.2021.100066>.
- [27] D. Vujović and N. Todorović, "An assessment of pollutant emissions due to air traffic at Nikola Tesla International Airport, Belgrade, and the link between local air quality and weather types," *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, vol. 56, pp. 85–94, Oct. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2017.08.003>.
- [28] A. Ashok, H. Balakrishnan, and S. R. H. Barrett, "Reducing the air quality and CO₂ climate impacts of taxi and takeoff operations at airports," *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, vol. 54, pp. 287–303, Jul. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2017.05.013>.
- [29] "Bucharest Airports - National Company Bucharest Airports - Air Traffic Statistics." <https://www.bucharestairports.ro/cnab/en/general-info/air-traffic-statistics>.

Document Co-citation Analysis using the Concept Lattice

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ABSTRACT

Document Co-citation Analysis (DCA) is a method to identify and analyze the relationships between co-cited documents. In this paper, we attempt to use concept lattice for DCA. Concept lattice is a graph structure given in Formal Concept Analysis (FCA), a branch of mathematics based on the concept and its hierarchy. The experiments are conducted on an extensive repository of citations extracted from DBLP, ACM, MAG (Microsoft Academic Graph), and other sources, having a total of 5,354,309 papers and 48,227,950 citation relationships. In this paper, it is established that the concept lattice supports DCA and helps to identify a set of co-cited documents and their co-citation strength. It also provides navigation to reflect the subset-superset relationship of the co-citations. Further, the concept lattice helps identify the hierarchy among the documents and answers the most relevant queries related to DCA.

Keywords-Document Co-citation Analysis (DCA); concept lattice; co-citation strength; citation dataset

I. INTRODUCTION

A citation is a reference to a document, a book, a publication, or an article. The analysis of such citations to understand the relationships and patterns between the documents, authors, keywords, or journals is termed as citation analysis [1-4]. It helps studying the importance and relevance of the work done by others, studying the trends of research, knowing about evolving areas of research, evolving journals in a specific area, etc. [5-10]. The cited work is the document mentioned in the reference and the citing work is the one which is referencing the cited work. DCA is a method to study the relationship among the documents based on the citations [1-4]. Two or more documents are said to be co-cited when they are

referenced by the same document. Co-citation strength measures the strength of the relationship between two documents based on the co-citation frequency [4]. For example, if two documents D and E, are cited by documents A, B, and C, then documents D, and E, are co-cited and have a co-citation strength of 3 (Table I). DCA is a process to discover co-cited documents along with their co-citation strength. The discovered co-citations are examined to find emerging patterns. The process helps to understand the connections and the similarities between different research areas [5-10]. It helps to identify the related research directions, the most influential work done by others, the most cited sub-themes within a particular theme, the evolution of new academic areas, etc. [6-8].

A concept lattice is a graph structure used in FCA to represent the relationships between concepts in a given context [11-13]. FCA is a mathematical field based on the graph structure which has been explored in the area of data analysis, knowledge representation, and information management [11-15]. In FCA, the elements of the graph are called Concepts, the lattice of the Concepts is a hierarchical structure of the Concepts which represents the hierarchy based on shared properties or attributes. A Concept has two components (Extent, Intent), where Extent is the set of objects and Intent is the set of attributes. For example, the concept lattice for the dataset given in Table I is shown in Figure 1. Seven Concepts have been identified, namely (ABC, DE), (ABCD, E), (CE, F), (DEF, G), (D,EG), (E,FG), (C, DEF).

TABLE I. SAMPLE CITATION DATASET

Document	References
A	D, E
B	D, E
C	D, E, F
D	E, G
E	F, G
F	G

Fig. 1. The concept lattice of the dataset given in Table I.

A. Our Contribution

DCA is an established powerful means for analyzing the relationships between a set of documents. Researchers working in the area of FCA have established the concept lattice structure as a means of analyzing the hierarchy of Concepts based on shared properties. Our contribution is an effort to establish a connection between FCA and DCA. For example, let us consider the dataset given in Table I and the concept lattice generated from this dataset shown in Figure 1. We can observe that a node in the concept lattice has (Extent, Intent) where Extent is showing the citing papers and Intent is showing the cited papers. The documents of the Intent are co-cited documents with the co-citation strength equal to the number of documents in the Extent. For example, the Intent having documents D and E has the Extent having documents A, B, C. Thus, documents D, and E, are co-cited with a co-citation strength equal to 3. This establishes the relationship between concept lattice and document co-citation. To the best of our knowledge, not much work has been done in this area.

B. Why FCA?

The concept lattice structure of FCA is an efficient tool for knowledge and knowledge discovery. The advantage of using concept lattice for DCA is that the concept lattice provides a hierarchical view of the co-citations. It provides navigation to reflect the subset-superset relationship of the co-citations. The rest of the paper is based on an analysis of concept lattice to answer the following queries related to document co-citation on the large citation network dataset downloaded from [16] and identify trends and useful patterns, such as:

- Most cited publications
- List of all co-cited publications.
- Co-citation strength of all co-cited publications.
- Evolution of new academic fields.
- The pattern of co-cited publications year-wise.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Collection and Software Used

There are various software applications available for generating the concept lattice [17]. The citation dataset was extracted from [16] and Charm software [18] was chosen to discover the concept lattice.

B. Pre-processing of the Available Citation Data

Pre-processing of the available citation data was done to provide the input to the concept lattice software, and the output of the software was interpreted for citation analysis. The data were in json format which was converted to text format. Two columns, namely id and references, were extracted. The id represents the publication/paper id and the reference has the list of cited publications. The extracted columns were converted to a file in the format desired by the Charm software. The data were huge to be kept in memory, so they were converted to smaller files and all the operations were performed on individual files and the results were combined. So, Charm software was run on the two columns of the citation dataset and the concept lattice was generated from that. A sample format of those two columns is shown in Table II.

TABLE II. SAMPLE FORMAT OBTAINED FROM THE CITATION DATASET

Paper Id: References
id1: id4, id5, id7
id2: id1, id4, id5
id3: id2
id4: id76, id5
id5: id1, id4, id5

Here, the publication with id1 cites three papers (id4, id5, id7). id1 and id4 are co-cited by id2 and id5. Hence the set (id1, id4) are co-cited documents with strength equal to two. Charm software is used to create a concept lattice from the publicly available dataset in [16] which has more than 6 million papers and citations. The features are extracted from the mentioned dataset and then Charm is run on those two features. No new dataset was created.

C. Generation of the Concept Lattice

When the concept lattice software Charm was run, an appropriate minimum support threshold was chosen after experimentation. The dataset has 3926533 rows (transactions) with 5347758 columns (items) after data cleaning. Discovering concepts from such a large dataset is a difficult task. So, we chose a minimum support threshold to find the frequent concepts. We experimented with different values. Finally, we selected 0.0001%, i.e. 393 transactions, as the minimum support threshold.

D. Exploration of the Concept Lattice

The generated concept lattice was analyzed to understand the thematic structure and the relationships between concepts. The most significant or influential concepts within the lattice were identified. This can help uncover key themes or research areas within the document collection.

E. Result Interpretation

The output is the lattice of concepts (Extent, Intent), where Intent is the list of co-cited publications, and Extent is the list of citing papers. Original Python code was written to extract the relevant information from the lattice, and present the same in informative manner. The Concepts and their relationships within the lattice were interpreted to gain insight into the intellectual structure of the field. The connections between different concepts were explored along with their associated documents to identify emerging research trends, influential works, and potential research gaps.

III. RESULTS

A. Dataset

The data were extracted from [16]. Different versions of this dataset are available in different formats [19-21]. For this project, version 13, which is stored in json format, was chosen. Version 13 of the data has 5,354,309 papers, and 48,227,950 citation relationships. The downloaded file has a size of 17.35 GB.

B. Data Description

The downloaded dataset has the characteristics shown in Table III. After processing the provided dataset, a large number of Concepts were generated. We summarized the results based on the number of publications in Intent (co-cited publications). The Extent of the Concept stores the publication ids of the citing papers. The frequency of the Extent is the co-citation strength. The summary of the results provides interesting insight about that data. The maximum number of publications in a set of co-cited publications is 6, and there is only one such set whose co-citation strength is 431. Similar to this, there are 13 sets of 5 co-cited publications, 67 sets of 4, 251 set of 3, and 997 sets of 2. Each of such set has different co-citation strength. The results are summarized in Table IV.

C. Most Cited Publications

As the number of publications in the set of co-cited publications increases, the co-citation strength decreases. Hence, the first level nodes of the lattice with one publication are the most cited publications. There 7955 such nodes. We can

sort them according to their frequency, and get the top cited references. Table V shows one such list of the top 10 most cited papers.

TABLE III. CITATION DATASET DESCRIPTION

Name	Type	Description
id	string	Paper id
title	string	Paper title
authors.name	string	Author name
author.org	string	Author affiliation
author.id	string	Author ID
venue.id	string	Paper venue ID
venue.raw	string	Paper venue name
year	int	Published year
keyword	list of strings	Keywords
fos.name	string	Fields of study
fos.w	float	Fields of study weight
references	list of strings	Paper references
ncitation	int	Citation number
pagestart	string	Page start
pageend	string	Page end
doctype	string	Paper type: journal, book title
lang	string	Detected language
publisher	string	Publisher
volume	string	Volume
issue	string	Issue
issn	string	Issn
isbn	string	Isbn
doi	string	doi
pdf	string	pdf URL
url	list	pdf URL
abstract	string	Abstract
indexedabstract	dict	Indexed abstract

TABLE IV. CO-CITED SETS IN THE CITATION DATASET

No. of publications in a co-cited set	Number of co-cited sets
1	7955
2	997
3	251
4	67
5	13
6	1

TABLE V. TOP 10 CITED PUBLICATIONS

Freq	Title	Year	References
26,873	Deep Residual Learning for Image Recognition	2016	36
24,814	ImageNet Classification with Deep Convolutional Neural Networks	2012	20
24,040	Distinctive Image Features from Scale-Invariant Keypoints	2004	33
20,464	LIBSVM: A library for support vector machines	2011	36
16,999	Long short-term memory	1997	27
14,684	Histograms of Oriented Gradients for Human Detection	2005	15
14,450	Latent dirichlet allocation	2001	15
12,998	Image quality assessment: from error visibility to structural similarity.	2004	29
12,220	Support-Vector Networks	1995	3
12,067	MapReduce: simplified data processing on large clusters	2008	18

D. List of All Co-Cited Publications

Table IV lists down the number of co-cited publications having 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6 publications. These data were derived from the generated lattice. So there are 1329 sets of co-cited publications.

E. Co-Citation Strength

The nodes of the generated lattice have the Extent and Intent fields, as mentioned above. Finding the cardinality of the Extent gives the co-citation strength of the related set. Further, we can find the top n number of co-citations having 2, 3, 4, 5, or 6 publications, and their corresponding co-citation strength.

F. Evolution of New Academic Fields

The lattice of publications yielded 9284 nodes, each representing one Concept. There were six levels of nodes where each level has that many numbers of publications in the Intent of the node representing the Concept. The set of 6 co-cited publications had small co-citation strength, so for further analysis, we chose a set of 5 co-cited publications. Out of 13

such sets, we chose the set having maximum co-citation strength. Let us denote that set as S . The paper ids of the publications of set S are shown in Table VI.

TABLE VI. PAPER IDS OF THE PUBLICATIONS IN THE SET S

573696056e3b12023e5186fe
556f622a2401b4b38c23635c
573696f46e3b12023e5f1198
573696026e3b12023e516718
5736986b6e3b12023e730129

Since the paper id is a long string, we are using the first 8 characters of those ids for any further reference. We chose a subset of the complete lattice. Figure 2 shows the subset having the paper ids given in Table VI. Each node of the lattice represents a Concept (Extent, Intent). For the co-cited publications in S , the number of publications in the Extent are 748. Since it is not possible to show all the publications of the Extent, a node of the lattice in Figure 2 represents (Intent, f) where Intent stores the list of co-cited publications, and f is the cardinality of the Extent representing the co-citation strength.

Fig. 2. Lattice of 5 co-cited publications in set S .

- [10] Z. A. Shaikh, "Keyword Detection Techniques: A Comprehensive Study," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 2590–2594, Feb. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1813>.
- [11] M. Kaytoue, S. O. Kuznetsov, and A. Napoli, "Revisiting Numerical Pattern Mining with Formal Concept Analysis," in *Proceedings of the Twenty-Second International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, 2011, pp. 1342–1347, <http://doi.org/10.5591/978-1-57735-516-8/IJCAI11-227>.
- [12] U. Priss, S. Polovina, and R. Hill, Eds., *Conceptual Structures: Knowledge Architectures for Smart Applications: 15th International Conference on Conceptual Structures, ICCS 2007, Sheffield, UK, July 22-27, 2007. Proceedings*, vol. 4604. Berlin, Heidelberg, Germany: Springer, 2007.
- [13] B. Ganter and R. Wille, *Formal Concept Analysis: Mathematical Foundations*. Berlin, Heidelberg, Germany: Springer Science & Business Media, 2012.
- [14] Y. Bastide, N. Pasquier, R. Taouil, G. Stumme, and L. Lakhal, "Mining Minimal Non-redundant Association Rules Using Frequent Closed Itemsets," in *Computational Logic — CL 2000*, London, UK, 2000, pp. 972–986, https://doi.org/10.1007/3-540-44957-4_65.
- [15] N. Pasquier, Y. Bastide, R. Taouil, and L. Lakhal, "Pruning closed itemset lattices for association rules," in *BDA'1998 international conference on Advanced Databases*, Hammamet, Tunisia, Oct. 1998, pp. 177–196.
- [16] "Citation Network Dataset: DBLP+Citation, ACM Citation network." <https://www.aminer.org/citation>.
- [17] "FCA Software." <https://upriss.github.io/fca/fcasoftware.html>.
- [18] M. J. Zaki, "CHARM Algorithm." Jul. 14, 2022, [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/zakimjz/CHARM>.
- [19] J. Tang, D. Zhang, and L. Yao, "Social Network Extraction of Academic Researchers," in *Proceedings of the 2007 Seventh IEEE International Conference on Data Mining*, USA, Jul. 2007, pp. 292–301, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDM.2007.30>.
- [20] J. Tang, J. Sun, C. Wang, and Z. Yang, "Social influence analysis in large-scale networks," in *Proceedings of the 15th ACM SIGKDD international conference on Knowledge discovery and data mining*, New York, NY, USA, Mar. 2009, pp. 807–816, <https://doi.org/10.1145/1557019.1557108>.
- [21] A. Sinha *et al.*, "An Overview of Microsoft Academic Service (MAS) and Applications," in *Proceedings of the 24th International Conference on World Wide Web*, New York, NY, USA, Feb. 2015, pp. 243–246, <https://doi.org/10.1145/2740908.2742839>.

Real-Time Fire and Smoke Detection for Trajectory Planning and Navigation of a Mobile Robot

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ABSTRACT

Mobile robots have many industrial applications, including security, food service, and fire safety. Detecting smoke and fire quickly for early warning and monitoring is crucial in every industrial safety system. In this paper, a method for early smoke and fire detection using mobile robots equipped with cameras is presented. The method employs artificial intelligence for trajectory planning and navigation, and focus is given to detection and localization techniques for mobile robot navigation. A model of a mobile robot with Omni wheels and a modified YOLOv5 algorithm for fire and smoke detection is also introduced, which is integrated into the control system. This research addresses the issue of distinct objects of the same class by assigning each object a unique identification. The implementation not only detects fire and smoke but also identifies the position of objects in three-dimensional space, allowing the robot to map its environment incrementally for mobile navigation. The experimental results demonstrate the high accuracy achieved by the proposed method in identifying smoke and fire.

Keywords-mobile robots; robot mapping; smoke and fire real-time detection; dynamic environment; localization; presumptive environment; robot navigation; object identification

I. INTRODUCTION

The accurate navigation of autonomous vehicles depends on precise information about the robot's state and surroundings,

including position, orientation, speed, and acceleration. While GPS is widely used for position estimation, it can be limited by environmental conditions and sensor cost. To address these limitations, a camera-based method for position estimation that

eliminates the reliance on GPS is proposed. This method utilizes visual information to improve accuracy and reduce cost in autonomous vehicle navigation. Cameras with depth sensors, such as monocular, stereoscopic, or omnidirectional cameras, can be used in different localization strategies. These strategies include map-building systems, map-based systems, and maple systems [1]. While SLAM and deep learning-based approaches have been proposed for path planning, they may not adequately handle dynamic environments. To address this, we present a visual-based localization approach implemented through a deep learning architecture in this article. Furthermore, we propose a method that utilizes a camera equipped with YOLOv5 + object tracking for detecting and tracking objects like fire and smoke, enabling the construction of 3D maps of these objects. Through this method, the robot can navigate towards the identified location of the fire.

II. RELATED WORK

There is a growing interest in the field of smoke and fire detection, primarily due to its significant applications in various domains. Detecting smoke and fire in its early stages plays a vital role in preventing potential disasters and minimizing associated damages. As a result, researchers are extensively investigating and developing innovative techniques and algorithms to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of smoke and fire detection systems. A large body of related work exists in this domain, spanning across multiple disciplines such as computer vision, image processing, machine learning, and sensor technology. Early approaches primarily focused on using traditional image processing methods, relying on color-based features and intensity transformations. In addition, smoke, temperature, or gas sensors can also be used for the purpose of early fire detection. For instance, authors in [2] used an MQ-5 sensor to continuously monitor the surrounding environment and prevent gas leakage, thus reducing the risk of fire and damage [2]. On the other hand, as mentioned above, a feasible method can be used to detect smoke using several techniques such as Haar features, Bhattacharya distance method, SIFT descriptors, Gabor wavelets approach, and SVM classifier to identify the smoke through video processing [3].

Regarding object tracking algorithms, this method is commonly used to track and detect objects, such as the implementation in [4] which combines the Scale Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT) and Singular Spectrum Analysis (SSA) methods. Based on these results, we propose utilizing a combination of the YOLOv5 deep learning model with object tracking algorithms to detect and provide early alerts of fires in real-time through a camera.

III. PROPOSED APPROACH

A. Object Detection with the Modified YOLOv5 Model

The YOLOv5 network consists of three main components, namely the backbone, neck, and head. The backbone is responsible for aggregating and generating image features from various fine-grained images through a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). The neck, on the other hand, comprises a series of network layers that mix and combine these image features and transfer them to the prediction layer. Finally, the

head utilizes the image features to produce bounding boxes and predict the categories of objects. To create different versions of the YOLOv5 network model, the width and depth of the backbone network are adjusted using the parameters `depth_multiple` and `width_multiple`. These adjustments result in 4 versions termed as YOLOv5x, YOLOv5l, YOLOv5m, and YOLOv5s. Among these versions, YOLOv5s is the simplest, with a `depth_multiple` of 0.33 and `width_multiple` of 0.5 [5]. It has the least model parameters and offers the fastest detection speed.

The purpose of the SPP (Spatial Pyramid Pooling) structure [6] in YOLOv5 network is to generate a fixed size feature vector as the output of a fully connected layer, regardless of the input image size. The SPP structure utilizes three convolution kernels with sizes of 3, 5, and 9, in order to extract features through the use of maximum pooling. This enhances the expressive capability of the feature graph and expands the network's receptive field. Figure 1(a) illustrates the SPP structure, which first applies 1×1 , 3×3 , 5×5 , and 9×9 maximum pooling operations to the data transferred from the convolutional normalization activation function (Convolution + Batch Normalization + SiLU (Sigmoid Linear Unit), CBS (Conv-BN-SiLU)) in parallel. These results are then joined to the CBS structure using concatenation splicing to accomplish feature fusion and complete the feature extraction process. However, the original SPP structure increases the computational workload due to the parallel pooling operations with differently-sized convolutional kernels, which affects performance. As a result, the Spatial Pyramid Pooling Fast (SPPF) structure is introduced to improve the pooling performance while reducing computational requirements. The SPPF structure substitutes the parallel maximum pooling operation from three convolutional kernels with different sizes in the original SPP, with a sequential operation using three convolutional kernels of the same size. As depicted in Figure 1, the SPPF structure bears resemblance to the SPP structure. Initially, the SPPF layer conducts a successive 5×5 maximum pooling operation on the data obtained from the CBS structure [7]. Subsequently, the data are merged into the CBS structure through concatenation splicing, enabling acceleration in processing speed while simultaneously obtaining a more comprehensive feature extraction.

Fig. 1. (a) SPP structure diagram and (b) SPPF structure diagram.

Authors in [5] made some modifications to the SPP module with quite promising results. However, with the proposed multi-scale architecture of SPPD, there may be some difficulties such as more complex computations for the computer. With the embedded Jetson Nano computer, we need a lightweight model that still maintains faster recognition speed. Therefore, it is necessary to modify the YOLOv5 model by reducing the number of max pooling layers and replacing the activation function with Leaky ReLU (Leaky Rectified Linear Unit) in the SPPF module. Modifying the YOLOv5 model may have some impacts on the model. Some possible impacts are the reduction of the number of max pooling layers. Max pooling is a transformation that not only reduces the size of feature maps but also decreases the accuracy of features by selecting the maximum value within the max pooling region. Reducing the number of max pooling layers can help retain more detailed information about the object's positions in the image. The advantages of replacing SiLU with Leaky ReLU can be described as:

- No gradient vanishing problem: The biggest advantage of Leaky ReLU over SiLU is that it avoids the issue of the gradient approaching zero. In SiLU, the derivative of the activation function is nearly zero as the input value approaches infinity, making backpropagation difficult and leading to gradient loss. On the other hand, with Leaky ReLU, the gradient does not vanish and can be easily propagated, helping improve training efficiency.
- Ability to learn complex models: Leaky ReLU allows the model to learn more complex non-linear properties by introducing negative outputs. This helps the model capture non-linear transformations in the data, while increasing flexibility and modeling ability.
- Positivity and fast computation: The Leaky ReLU activation function simply multiplies negative inputs by a small non-zero coefficient, while positive inputs remain unchanged. This makes the positivity of Leaky ReLU higher than SiLU. Moreover, the computation of Leaky ReLU is simpler than SiLU, which helps increase computation speed in the model.

Therefore, reducing the number of max pooling layers and replacing the activation function with leaky ReLU in the SPPF module of YOLOv5 can improve the model's object recognition capability and help the model converge better during training. Figure 2 shows the modified SPPF module of YOLOv5. Figure 3 demonstrates the training results of the modified YOLOv5 model.

Fig. 2. Modified SPPF structure.

Fig. 3. Model training graph.

Through training the model, we observed the accuracy and strength of the early fire detection model using the modified YOLOv5 algorithm. This enables early fire alerts to be efficiently and quickly triggered, thereby helping to prevent or minimize damage. The basic system meets the necessary accuracy requirements and avoids data overfitting, while the output probability meets the evaluation and early fire alert goals. After experimenting with the Jetson Nano Developer Kit, it was observed that the system can detect at a speed of about 62 frames per second, meeting the set target and utilizing the available devices we have.

B. Data Preparation and Processing

Detecting smoke accurately in practice is a challenging task due to complex possible scenarios and limited image information. Creating a training dataset with paired smoke images and bounding box positions is a major challenge for comprehensive learning. However, well-constructed datasets can effectively train discriminative models as smoke detectors, ensuring accurate detection of smoldering fires. The dataset Smoke 100k [9] was used with options such as high smoke, low smoke, and medium smoke. Fire data, including videos, were collected from the internet. Cleaning the data is crucial but time-consuming, involving removing irrelevant data, outliers, filling missing values, standardizing patterns, and ensuring data confidentiality. Once cleaned, validation is essential to test for errors in the preparation process. The validation step helps identifying any remaining issues that need to be addressed before moving forward. All collected data were divided into 3 categories corresponding for smoke and fire: low, medium, and high. However, to keep it simple in programming, we only used 2 labels: fire and smoke. After collecting the data, we labeled them using the online platform makesense.ai [8]. Subsequently, we converted the annotated image into a text format based on the YOLO format.

C. Object Tracking Algorithm

In this algorithm, we use object tracking in combination with YOLOv5. Object tracking is the task of automatically identifying objects in a video and calculating the trajectories of each object. Object tracking is often used in the surveillance fields such as automatic number plate recognition. So that, we can see the difference with usual object detection algorithms is YOLO does not distinguish objects of the same class and YOLOv5 + object tracking gives a unique id in each object.

Assumption: The detector produces a detection per frame for every object to be tracked. Detections of an object in consecutive frames have a high overlap rate.

$$IOU(S_1, S_2) = \frac{S_1 \cap S_2}{S_1 \cup S_2} \quad (1)$$

Inputs:

$$\{D_0, D_1, \dots, D_{F-1}\} = \left\{ \begin{matrix} \{d_0, d_1, \dots, d_{N-1}\}, \{d_0, d_1, \dots, d_{N-1}\} \\ \dots \\ \{d_0, d_1, \dots, d_{N-1}\} \end{matrix} \right\} \quad (2)$$

where D_f represents the detections at frame f and d_j represents the j^{th} detection at that frame.

Figure 4 shows the flowchart of the proposed algorithm. To fully supervise the workspace, the robot's motion trajectory is determined based on the workspace. Figure 5 shows the robot's trajectory as it moves in the working environment, with coordinates determined by the encoder signal during its movement.

Fig. 4. Algorithm of YOLOv5 + object tracking.

Fig. 5. The trajectory of the robot in the workspace and when fire is detected.

When a fire point is detected, the robot's trajectory is adjusted based on the distance and angle calculated using the stereo camera. To approach and alert the fire point, the trajectory changes to a vector with the robot's position at the detection point as the starting point and the location of the fire as the endpoint.

D. Navigation

The robot has omni wheels to enhance its flexibility when operating within the workspace. Moreover, the omni wheels, in combination with the three-wheeled robot structure, are highly suitable for adjusting the camera's vision flexibly. During movement, based on the omnidirectional nature of the omni wheels, the robot can follow the desired trajectories or rotate at desired angles in a stationary position. This not only enables the robot to fast and flexibly reach fire-risk locations but also facilitates camera vision adjustments. In this way, the camera can be directed more directly toward the fire location, thus enhancing the accuracy of the fire hazard recognition model.

The robot navigates along the predetermined trajectory, enabling it to perform monitoring tasks and alerting upon fire detection. The starting position serves as the initial point, and if no fire is detected, the robot continues to navigate throughout the supervised area. The completion of a navigation cycle is indicated when the robot returns to its initial position. This navigation process is repeated in the absence of fire detections. When a fire is detected, the robot must accurately navigate along a new trajectory to make a θ degree turn and move a distance of d .

The multi-directional robot using omni wheels is described in [10]. The robot is positioned within the $(O_w \hat{X}_w \hat{Z}_w)$ coordinate system. This mobile robot consists of the robot body and three omnidirectional wheels labeled 1, 2, and 3. The wheels are arranged equidistantly from the center of the robot chassis with a spacing of 120 degrees. The parameters for an omnidirectional mobile robot are:

M_r : the total mass of the mobile robot, including the robot's body mass and the components' mass.

L_c : the radius of the mobile robot.

f_1, f_2, f_3 : the reaction force applied by the ground to the omni-directional wheel, where the direction is vertical to wheel axes 1, 2, and 3, respectively

R_w : the radius of the omni-directional wheels.

δ_C : the angle between wheel 2 and the \hat{Z}_M -axis of the mobile coordinate system.

ϕ : the rotation angle of the omnidirectional mobile robot.

I_y : the moment of inertia of the omni-directional mobile robot about the \hat{Y}_M -axis.

$\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3$: the rotation angle of omni-directional wheel 1, 2, and 3, respectively.

$\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3$: the angular velocity of omni-directional wheels 1, 2, and 3, respectively.

$[Z_W \ X_W]^T$: the position of the center of mass of the robot relative to the coordinate system.

The dynamics and kinematics of the mobile robot can be described by:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{z}_w \\ \dot{x}_w \\ \dot{\phi} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} M_t & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & M_t & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & I_y \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \cos \phi & -\sin \phi & 0 \\ \sin \phi & \cos \phi & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -0.5 & -0.5 \\ 0 & \sqrt{3}/2 & -\sqrt{3}/2 \\ L_c & L_c & L_c \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{z}_w \\ \dot{x}_w \\ \dot{\phi} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where $\dot{z}_w, \dot{x}_w, \dot{\phi}$ are the recent coordinates of the robot, determined by input parameters like $M_t, I_y, \sin \phi, \cos \phi$, and L_c . Equation (14) describes the relationship between these parameters.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \omega_1 \\ \omega_2 \\ \omega_3 \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{R_w} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & L_c \\ -0.5 & \sqrt{3}/2 & L_c \\ -0.5 & -\sqrt{3}/2 & L_c \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \cos \phi & \sin \phi & 0 \\ -\sin \phi & \cos \phi & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{z}_w \\ \dot{x}_w \\ \dot{\phi} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Based on the recent coordinates of the robot, the velocity in each wheel is calculated by (14). We can see that the velocity in each wheel depends on the radius of the Omni directional wheel. In the first matrix, the 3x3 parameters of the matrix are $\frac{1}{2}; -\frac{1}{2}; \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}; -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}; 0$ created by the initial angle (30 degrees) and the radius of the robot. The next 3x3 matrix is created by rotating by angle θ and the final 1x3 matrix is based on the recent robot coordinates. The omnidirectional wheels in this study were powered by DC servo motors. The model for a DC motor can be simplified to:

$$\tau_m = \frac{K_t}{R_a} u - \frac{K_t^2}{R_a} \omega_m \quad (5)$$

where τ_m is the motor torque, calculated by u which is the control voltage, K_t is the motor torque constant, ω_m is the angular velocity of the motor, and R_a is the armature resistance. The traction force f of the wheel is given by the calculated motor torque [11]:

$$f = \frac{n}{R_w} \tau_m \quad (6)$$

where n is the gear ratio. The three motors used in this mobile robot are identical. Therefore, combining (5) and (6), the relationship between f_1, f_2, u , and ω is given by:

$$[f_1 \ f_2 \ f_3]^T = \frac{nK_t}{R_w R_a} [u_1 \ u_2 \ u_3]^T - \frac{n^2 K_t^2}{R_w R_a} [\omega_1 \ \omega_2 \ \omega_3]^T \quad (7)$$

The dynamics of the robot can be presented as:

$$\ddot{P}_\omega = A_\omega \dot{P}_\omega + B_\omega(\phi) U_C \quad (8)$$

where:

$$P_\omega = [z_w \ x_w \ \phi]^T \quad (9)$$

$$U_C = [u_1 \ u_2 \ u_3]^T \quad (10)$$

$$a_1 = \frac{-3n^2 K_t^2}{2R_w^2 M_t R_a} \quad (11)$$

$$a_2 = \frac{-3n^2 K_t^2 L_c^2}{R_w^2 I_y R_a} \quad (12)$$

$$b_1 = \frac{nK_t}{2R_w M_t R_a} \quad (13)$$

$$b_2 = \frac{nK_t L_c}{R_w I_y R_a} \quad (14)$$

$$A_\omega = \begin{bmatrix} a_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & a_1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & a_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

$$B_\omega(\phi) = \begin{bmatrix} 2b_1 \cos \phi & -b_1 \cos \phi - \sqrt{3}b_1 \sin \phi & -b_1 \cos \phi + \sqrt{3}b_1 \sin \phi \\ 2b_1 \sin \phi & -b_1 \sin \phi + \sqrt{3}b_1 \cos \phi & -b_1 \sin \phi - \sqrt{3}b_1 \cos \phi \\ b_2 & b_2 & b_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

We assume that the predicted fire-point of the ball in the $(O_w \ \hat{X}_w \ \hat{Z}_w)$ coordinate system is $[z_{bw}(t) \ x_{bw}(t)]^T$. The position reference to the mobile robot is set to be:

$$P_{bw}(t) = [z_{bw}(t) \ x_{bw}(t) \ \phi]^T \quad (17)$$

where the rotation angle ϕ is assumed to be 0. The tracking error is defined as:

$$e(t) = P_{bw}(t) - P_\omega(t) \quad (18)$$

The tracking error is definitely important because of its role in the PID controller, which is described by:

$$u(t) = K_p e(t) + K_i \int_0^t e(t) dt + K_d e(t) \frac{d}{dt} \quad (19)$$

From $e(t)$, \ddot{e} can be given by:

$$\ddot{e} = \ddot{P}_{bw} - [A_\omega \dot{P}_\omega + B_\omega(\phi) U_C] \quad (20)$$

The definition of a new control input U is:

$$U \triangleq \ddot{P}_{bw} - [A_w \dot{P}_w + B_w(\phi)U_C] \quad (21)$$

From the above, we obtain:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} e \\ \dot{e} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & I \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} e \\ \dot{e} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ I \end{bmatrix} U \quad (22)$$

The feedback control U_C can be written as:

$$U_C = B_w(\phi)^{-1} [\ddot{P}_{bw} - A_w \dot{P}_w - U] \quad (23)$$

In (23), the system is decoupled into a linear form, and the PID control algorithm is employed to achieve tracking control and calibrate the speed as expected. Consequently, the subsequent PID control strategy applies in this scenario:

$$\dot{e} = e \text{ and } U = -K_p e - K_d \dot{e} - K_i \varepsilon \quad (24)$$

where K_d , K_p , and K_i are 3×3 diagonal PID gain matrices with equal $\text{diag}\{k_{d_i}\}$, $\text{diag}\{k_{p_i}\}$, and $\text{diag}\{k_{i_i}\}$, respectively, and $i = 1, 2, 3$. The closed-loop tracking error system using PID controller is given by:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon \\ e \\ \dot{e} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & I & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & I \\ -K_i & -K_p & -K_d \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon \\ e \\ \dot{e} \end{bmatrix} \quad (25)$$

According to the Routh–Hurwitz criterion, PID gain values k_p , k_i , and k_d must satisfy: $k_i < k_d k_p$, $i = 1, 2, 3$.

Fig. 6. Rotation and movement of the robot.

The PID control gain values are determined using the proposed control method in order to achieve closed-loop stability. The phase margin and gain margin have been set to 45° . The maneuverability and controllability of a 3-omni wheel robot are inversely related. The robot exhibits exceptional maneuverability due to the flexibility of its omni wheels. However, precise control is necessary to maintain trajectory accuracy and prevent unwanted movements. To achieve this, encoders are installed on each driving motor of the robot to measure wheel speed and distance traveled. In the event of fire detection, the robot's trajectory is modified, and navigation is required to guide the robot along the new path towards the fire.

The Jetson Nano and stereo camera determine the distance d and angle θ and the robot rotates by θ degrees and moves straight for the distance d based on this information (Figure 6).

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The omni-directional 3-wheel robot successfully detected smoke and fire, navigated to their location utilizing a camera and YOLOv5 algorithm. Object tracking algorithms enabled the tracking of these objects across multiple frames with the help of a camera and Jetson Nano developer kit for detection and processing. Once an object is detected, YOLOv5 identifies its type and provides positional information. The object tracking algorithm tracks the object across frames and calculates the optimal path. With advanced algorithms and information processing, the robot can navigate accurately and safely toward the source of smoke or fire. This feature is valuable in emergency and firefighting scenarios. The results can be demonstrated using an embedded computer connected to a screen, enabling the robot to adjust its trajectory based on fire recognition signals captured by the camera (Figures 7-8). Figure 7 was captured after completing the trajectory change and reaching the fire detection point. In Figure 8, the robot follows a pre-programmed path, but alters its trajectory towards the detected fire location once it receives the camera signal.

Fig. 7. The result after the robot detects fire and moves to the fire point.

Fig. 8. Initial trajectory, change in trajectory, and movement to the fire location.

V. CONCLUSION

The current research has successfully developed an autonomous omni-directional robot equipped with a camera for navigation and early fire detection. The proposed method enables the robot to detect smoke and fire, calculate the

trajectory, and accurately navigate to the smoke/fire location. The control of the robot model moving along the trajectory is performed precisely according to the kinematics and dynamics problems. By applying the versatility of the omni wheels, the robot moves flexibly and accurately. In addition, the use of modified YOLOv5 in combination with object tracking provides a new solution for object recognition. The model's verification in fire and smoke detection has proven that YOLOv5 performs considerably better than the original model, with an accuracy of up to 95% on our fire and smoke dataset. Moreover, the enhanced YOLOv5 can detect 62 frames per second, meeting real-time demands. The omni robot has demonstrated its ability to identify and locate smoke and fire using the camera, YOLOv5, and object tracking. This advancement holds promise for various applications in robotics technology. However, the trajectory planning method used in this research may not have a high success rate in handling obstacles near the target location. Future work could focus on addressing this limitation to enhance the overall performance of the system.

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REFERENCES

- [1] M. S. Güzel, "Autonomous Vehicle Navigation Using Vision and Mapless Strategies: A Survey," *Advances in Mechanical Engineering*, vol. 5, Jan. 2013, Art. no. 234747, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/234747>.
- [2] B. F. Alshammari and M. T. Chughtai, "IoT Gas Leakage Detector and Warning Generator," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 6142–6146, Aug. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3712>.
- [3] P. Matlani and M. Shrivastava, "An Efficient Algorithm Proposed For Smoke Detection in Video Using Hybrid Feature Selection Techniques," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 3939–3944, Apr. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2571>.
- [4] A. Ozturk and I. Cayiroglu, "A Real-Time Application of Singular Spectrum Analysis to Object Tracking with SIFT," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 8872–8877, Aug. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5022>.
- [5] Z. Wu, R. Xue, and H. Li, "Real-Time Video Fire Detection via Modified YOLOv5 Network Model," *Fire Technology*, vol. 58, no. 4, pp. 2377–2403, Jul. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10694-022-01260-z>.
- [6] K. He, X. Zhang, S. Ren, and J. Sun, "Spatial Pyramid Pooling in Deep Convolutional Networks for Visual Recognition," in *Computer Vision – ECCV 2014*, Cham, 2014, pp. 346–361, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-10578-9_23.
- [7] M. Qiu, L. Huang, and B.-H. Tang, "ASFF-YOLOv5: Multielement Detection Method for Road Traffic in UAV Images Based on Multiscale Feature Fusion," *Remote Sensing*, vol. 14, no. 14, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 3498, <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14143498>.
- [8] "Make Sense." <https://www.makesense.ai/>.
- [9] H.-Y. Cheng, J.-L. Yin, B.-H. Chen, and Z.-M. Yu, "Smoke 100k: A Database for Smoke Detection," in *2019 IEEE 8th Global Conference on Consumer Electronics (GCCE)*, Osaka, Japan, Jul. 2019, pp. 596–597, <https://doi.org/10.1109/GCCE46687.2019.9015309>.
- [10] S.-T. Kao and M.-T. Ho, "Ball-Catching System Using Image Processing and an Omni-Directional Wheeled Mobile Robot," *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 9, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 3208, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s21093208>.
- [11] M.-T. Ho and H.-S. Wang, "Pid Controller Design With Guaranteed Gain And Phase Margins," *Asian Journal of Control*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 374–381, 2003, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1934-6093.2003.tb00129.x>.

Design Improvement for a Maritime Training Polygon using 3D Terrestrial Laser Scanning Technology

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ABSTRACT

In the current geo-strategic context, the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) and the International Maritime Organization (IMO) impose increasingly high standards for seafarers' preparation in the ship's vitality training centers (elaborate constructions, designed and equipped specifically for training personnel in scenarios involving flooding and fires that may occur on board ships). The buildings housing these training areas experience considerable mechanical and thermal stress, which, over time, affects their structural integrity. Therefore, repairs and modernization work become necessary. This paper provides a case study on the application of technologies for terrestrial laser scanning of buildings, with a focus on the vitality training polygon. The originality of the approach comes from achieving "as-built" documentation for the vitality polygon using 3D laser scanning technology. This includes both three-dimensional modeling based on digital information from the scanning process, as well as structural analysis using finite element techniques for the buildings where crew training takes place. The study also analyzes the distribution of total deformations and stresses in the walls of exercise compartments for flooding and water fight scenarios. Moreover, temperature distribution in the walls and interior atmosphere of these compartments is examined for fire scenarios and firefighting.

Keywords-3D laser scanning; Building Information Modeling (BIM); finite element methods; mechanical and thermal analysis; flooding and firefighting

I. INTRODUCTION

Risk assessment for personnel involved in maritime transportation [1] is a priority topic and many operators are currently acting to improve their actions to reduce risk exposure. The risks considered are primarily those affecting the safety of the ships, transported goods, or embarked crews. Those who work in the field of marine engineering and navigation are well aware that the International Maritime Organization (IMO), as an entity concerned with sustainable development, has taken on the primary responsibility for the

safety and security of maritime transport, including ensuring the ship's vitality. We must not forget the strategies of the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) which, in the maritime field, has as priorities maritime security, freedom of navigation, and secure maritime trade routes [2]. The vitality of the ship refers to the maintenance of its architectural, functional, and operational characteristics (by ensuring all nautical qualities) in conditions of damage generated by water and fire. The fight to maintain the ship's vitality represents the organized effort of the crew, whether military and/or civilian. They use on-board installations systems and equipment to

mitigate the effects of water floods and to extinguish fires generated by various causes. The success of this action depends on the crew's understanding of the ship's construction and characteristics, the functioning of the onboard installation systems and equipment, as well as the appropriate measures to be taken when using them. The level of theoretical and practical training to be demonstrated by the personnel on board ships is regulated at the international level by:

- For military personnel, through NATO operational standards, which refer to the preparation of a compact, efficient, and flexible military force capable of meeting national and international security requirements.
- For civilian crews, through the requirements expressed in the International Convention on Standards of Training, Certification and Watchkeeping for Seafarers (STCW).

To efficiently train the personnel regarding the ship's vitality, specific arrangements are required, known by the

generic name of vitality simulators (or vitality polygons), properly organized and equipped for the fight against flooding and fire situations. In the most general way, vitality polygons must be provided with container modules for the execution of exercises with water and fire, placed and arranged in such a way as to simulate locations and routes possible to be encountered on board a ship. Inside the container modules, all the installations, equipment, and systems necessary for the simulation of the damage (flooding and/or fire) must be provided, as well as equipment for the individual protection of the participants in the simulation exercises (Figure 1). It is therefore imperative that the technical and qualitative level of the simulators for personnel training in the fight to ensure the vitality of the ship matches the level of technical and operational performance of vessels in both military and commercial fleets (characterized by new types of ships, with increasingly diverse and specific functionalities, equipped with sophisticated installations, systems and equipment and which must also meet the most rigorous demands in terms of safety and security).

Fig. 1. Exercises for the fight against flooding (left) and fire (right) situations.

Scientific research concerns regarding the use of 3D laser scanning techniques in the field of marine engineering are reflected in the literature through various publications. It's worth noting that these concerns remain constant, with specialized literature offering interested readers access to articles dating from 1997 to the present. It can also be found, with relative ease, that the field of applicability in marine engineering is extremely wide, starting from modern ships or underwater vehicles dedicated to offshore operations to port facilities. Additionally, this also holds true for domains such as shipbuilding, navigation, operation of offshore platforms or submarine pipelines, reaching as far as marine archaeology. To ensure an appropriate layout of the paper, selected articles related to the content of this work were considered. As the paper is dedicated to a case study, the literature review is brief. However, this does not imply that the topic lacks significance for researchers.

The high values of mechanical and thermal stress to which the buildings of vitality polygons are subjected rapidly erode their structural integrity, thus it is important to know which factors contribute to increasing the rate of deterioration (risk, design, structural components, materials used, quality of workforce) are and what intervention measures can be taken before material, financial and human losses occur [3]. The advantages of using Building Information Modeling (BIM) technology supported by high-performance tools (such as Auto Desk Revit 2020 and Auto Desk Insight 360) allow the creation

of complex 3D models but also bi-directional links with different components of documentation (views, sections, plans) thus reducing errors, saving worktime, and maintaining project accuracy [4].

The technology of three-dimensional (3D) laser scanning of buildings is a very efficient tool for drawing up "as-built" documentation. Compared to classical investigation and measurement technologies, laser scanning is fast, safe, does not require multiple work teams and does not involve significant expenses. The high accuracy of measurements and the substantial amount of digital Computer Aided Design (CAD) information that can be achieved with the help of this technology, enable the creation of intricate 3D models, according to the reality on the ground. Once created, the 3D models can be reconfigured into multiple variants and validated by structural analyses (mechanical, thermal, etc.) to justify the choice of the optimal solution and certify the quality and safety of the execution project. For reliable measurement of the structural element deformation caused by various loads (sometimes critical) [5], a new approach is presented to determine and measure the structural displacements, based on a numerical model whose accuracy may be assessed by using the least squares method and which provides more accurate results compared to the existing technologies and instruments of measurement. The use of high-speed laser scanners was highlighted in the literature quite early [6] in various fields, from mechanical engineering to optical engineering and

electronics being targeted both hardware and software approaches. In [6], the authors present a three-dimensional image projection system without the use of special viewing glasses. The technology involves the synchronization of laser beams (which determine plane coordinates) with the movement of a helical screen (which establishes the spatial, depth coordinate) thereby generating a true 3D image. Authors in [7] propose methodologies for 3D modeling of complex objects with a high degree of accuracy. They demonstrate the necessity for a hybrid approach that combines photogrammetry with laser scanning techniques. In 2010-2015, there was an increased interest in small, portable scanning tools, whose operational characteristics are similar to those of scanning stations. 3D laser scanners assert their usefulness in quality control and product design in marine engineering, facilitating the creation of new technical documentation in the form of CAD drawings. As a part of Reverse Engineering (RE), 3D scanning can create complex digital libraries and the integration of special software applications can greatly improve the scanning process and shorten modeling time. Authors in [8] propose a solution for transferring both the entire infrastructure (except for the physical measuring machines) and the software information into cloud computing, simplifying the scanning process and accelerating information exchange. A topic of interest is the digitization of existing paper documentation of entities previously built, requiring project modifications. Authors in [9] describe an interesting procedure (which can be extended to other types of entities encountered in marine engineering) for regenerating technical documentation (CAD drawings). By analyzing the shape of real-size vessels or mock-ups, using reverse engineering techniques, 3D modeling is facilitated by digital photogrammetry.

Laser scanning technology can be divided into two categories: static (when the scanner is held in a fixed position during data acquisition) and dynamic (when the scanner is mounted on a mobile platform). The use of dynamic laser scans in marine engineering offers the possibility of collecting information from offshore platforms or with the help of autonomous vehicles. In its contents, authors in [10] present the advantages offered by mobile marine scanning but also pay attention to errors caused by disturbances induced by the navigation environment (geometric characteristics, speed and direction of wave movement as well as the relative positioning of the mobile platform on which the scanner is located in relation to the wave front). Authors in [11] focused on factors affecting the accuracy of 3D laser scanning and highlighted errors concerning the scanned object which may be generated by external environmental disturbances, human intervention (sometimes non-professional) or limitations in measurement methods and instrument defects. Operational principles of terrestrial laser scanning for multi-story buildings (as is the case with the vitality polygon illustrated in the case study of this paper) were examined in [12] addressing both the analytical aspects of numerical modeling and the practical aspects of effective field measurement and scanning. Authors in [13] illustrate, how, with the help of terrestrial laser scanning, it is possible to digitize the already built structures as well as to modify the original project for the purpose of modernization, reconfiguration, or space rearrangement.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3D scanning is often used to produce "as-built" documentation or to carry out the measurements required for the design, construction or upgrading of the buildings, or installations specific to various fields. The "as built" implies the existence of an editable form of the files, that will be updated, according to the requirements. In the absence of the editable form, it is obvious that, first, all the drawings of the project must be redrawn, then the information be updated, resulting in the final form of the execution project. Laser scanning is a technique that involves sampling a surface using laser technology. The information collected can then be used to build 2D representations or 3D models, usable in a wide variety of applications. As mentioned above, laser scanning technology can be divided into two categories: static and dynamic. The advantages of using the static method arise from its high accuracy and relatively dense points cloud. These dynamic laser scanners require additional positioning systems such as Inertial Navigation System (INS) or Global Positioning System (GPS) which make the system more complex and expensive. 3D laser scanning captures thousands of points on the surface to be scanned in a very short time. The result of laser scanning is an organized 3D representation of recorded objects, called a points cloud. The points cloud obtained is subsequently processed in various applications (like Autodesk ReCap or Architecture, Engineering & Construction collection) to obtain accurate and high-precise 2D or 3D CAD representations. The advantages of 3D scanning are: precise and accurate information about the scanned object, scanning can be performed both day and night, outside or indoors, the scanned information can be accessed at any time, without another site visit, speed of measurements (thousands of points measured per second), and the possibility to scan the studied object from a safe distance, which leads to the avoidance of accidents. After 3D scanning, complete information about a building is obtained, allowing a complex analysis of it: facades, walls, floors etc. The analysis can be done starting from a simple study of the positioning and sizing of some elements, up to a complex qualitative analysis of the building in terms of decay, deformations, and possible cracks in the structural elements.

III. CASE STUDIES

An upgrade of an outdated firefighting and flood damage simulator is needed to ensure contemporary training facilities for the crews, students, and other personnel. The main objectives are: to train the skills and aptitudes of the navy categories of personnel in the fire fighting and flood damage onboard ship and to ensure the optimal conditions for the simulation with real scenarios during the practical training sessions. Considering the need for training in the field of ensuring the vitality of the ship to meet the urgency demanded by NATO standards and the requisites of the STCW code for the crews of military vessels, personnel embarked within commercial fleets and for military and civilian students, the project titled Modernization of the Vitality Polygon was proposed at the authors' academic institution. This project was approved for development during the period 2021-2024. The stated goal of the project is to provide modern, safe, and efficient training facilities in order to gain insight, skills and

expertise in ensuring the vitality of the ship for the embarked personnel, both military and civilian. The purpose of this paper is to present the results obtained in the first two years of the project. To carry out the project of upgrading the vitality simulator, the following steps were established.

A. Analysis of the Current State of the Vitality Polygon

The vitality polygon within the author's academic institution was put into operation in 1989, and is used for the training of civilian and military students and crews. The vitality polygon has the following structure: building A, intended for training activities in the fight against fire and water (Figure 2), building B, used for training activities involving crew members moving within compartments without visibility (Figure 3), and building C, designed for storing materials used in training activities in the fight against fire and water. At this stage, the deterioration of the equipment was identified, emphasizing the need to modernize the training facilities for the personnel,

Fig. 2. Building A of the vitality polygon.

Fig. 3. Building B of the vitality polygon.

Fig. 4. Example of laser scanning positions.

Figure 5 shows the "points cloud", unprocessed, outside and inside the complex, the remarkable accuracy of measurement and subsequent modeling possibilities being suggested.

matching them with the standards of the existing facilities in military and commercial fleets.

B. 3D Scanning of the Vitality Polygon

Scanning of the vitality complex was carried out by use of the Faro Focus 3D-X330 Laser Scanner, a high-speed 3D scanner with the following characteristics: extra-long range, integrated GPS, with a resolution of ± 2 mm and a range between 0.6 m and 330 m with HDR photo coverage. The 3D scanning process was considered for the outside and inside of the three buildings of the vitality polygon. Scanning was performed at a level of minimum accuracy of LOA30 according to the Guide for USIBD [14]. The 3D model complies with the Level of Development Specification 2020 (LOD 300) [15]. Figure 4 illustrates a visual representation of the scanning operations that highlights the positions of the laser beam fixation of the scanning instrument.

C. 3D Modeling of the New Vitality Polygon and Structural Analysis

After completing the 3D scanning process of the vitality polygon and the processing of points cloud, with the help of the SolidWorks Professional/Routing software, the three buildings of the vitality polygon were 3D modeled, its new structure being proposed. The proposed models must be evaluated in terms of the stresses (deformations, tensions) to which the building walls and the interior arrangements may be exposed during the various training exercises in the fight against water and fire. The following activities were conducted: the analysis of the total deformations and stress resistance of the building A structure when operating under maximum water load conditions and the analysis of thermal stresses at the walls of building B in temperature and humidity conditions established by the complex standard training exercises.

Fig. 5. Unprocessed points cloud, outdoor (left), indoor (right).

Fig. 6. 3D view of building A of the new vitality polygon.

For the above mentioned analyses, the Finite Element Method (FEM) was used and involved the following: geometrical modeling, domain discretization (which includes: construction of the network of finite elements, numbering of nodes and elements, and generating geometric properties), derivation of finite element equations, assembly of finite element equations, introduction of boundary conditions and reduction of the system of equations, solving the system of equations that describes the behavior of the studied structure, and post-processing. Obviously, 3D modeling and structural analysis steps are interconnected. The structural analysis of the proposed model assumes its remodeling until the final shape is established. In this paper, only the final models will be presented in the following sections.

1) Modeling and Structural Analysis of Building A

Building A, in its new configuration, will be dedicated to the fight against water (Figure 6). The interior partitioning and mesh of Building A resulted from the structural analyses seen in Figure 7. At the same time, the route of the flooding installation and the position of the leakage that generate the water fighting scenarios were established. Essentially, the equipment is represented by piping, manual and remotely operated valves, pumps, automation installation, signaling, etc.

Fig. 7. Interior partitioning and mesh of the new building A.

The mesh is specific to structural mechanical analysis, with a high level of accuracy (the maximum size of an element is 10 cm, having 689,899 nodes and 344,464 elements). The considered boundary conditions and loads are: maximum admissible tension for naval steel of 235 N/mm^2 with a safety coefficient of 10%, a force of 49 kN representing the ceiling of the structure, 2 forces of 3 kN each representing the action of water on the upper floor of the structure, the use of High-Energy Beams (HEB) at the bottom of the construction, a maximum level of 1.5 m for water height in the small training compartment. Figure 8 represents the distribution of the hydrostatic pressure force into the large training compartment.

Fig. 8. Hydrostatic pressure forces into the large compartment.

The study illustrates the variations of the total deformations and stresses on the structure under analysis. Three case studies were carried out.

- Case 1. The exercise is developed only in the small exercise compartment. Figure 9 emphasizes that the required standard limits are not exceeded (the maximum stress is 116.11 MPa).

Fig. 9. Distribution of the stresses for the small compartment.

- Case 2. The exercise is carried out in both compartments at the first level. The required standard limits are not exceeded, the maximum stresses being 184.81 MPa (Figure 10).

Fig. 10. Distribution of stresses for the compartments at the first level.

- Case 3. The exercise is developed in both compartments on the first level and with water in the compartments on the second level. As can be seen in Figure 11, the required standard limits are not exceeded in this situation either, the maximum stresses being 184.78 MPa.

Fig. 11. Distribution of stresses in the case of existence of water in the compartments on the second level.

In the project, several possible cases were simulated, depending on the type of exercise. This paper presents the three most unfavorable cases. The bottom line is that in the version with the highest load, the structure of building A of the vitality complex does not undergo structural changes.

2) Modeling and Structural Analysis of Building B

Building B, in its new configuration (Figure 12) will be dedicated to fighting fire. As in the case of building A, the inner partitioning of building B was determined through structural analysis and, furthermore, thermal analysis was conducted.

The routes of the water and foam fire extinguishing installation, the controlled fire production installation, the ventilation installation, and the support equipment have been established, to create the most realistic scenarios for combating fires. The firefighting training platform is represented by compartments with the greatest risk of onboard fire occurrences. The following section will present the results of the thermal analysis conducted for Building B, in the framework within which the action of heat emanating from the combustion of fuel (diesel) in a burner was studied.

Following the proposal for the modernization of building B, the metallic structure was obtained. Figure 13 is presented as an example.

For the thermal analysis of the walls of the compartment in which the burner is mounted, the construction was simplified, and the following hypotheses were taken into account: the cube inside the room represents the burner, on two sides it exhibits radiation resulting from the combustion of fuel while on the other two sides of the cube it exhibits radiation to the body of the burner and then heat transfers to the walls, smoke discharges are closed, and the ambient temperature is 20°C. Figure 14 illustrates the 3D model and the mesh of building B of the vitality polygon.

The mesh is one specific to fluid flows, with a high level of accuracy (the maximum size of an element is 25 cm, having 8317 nodes and 4631 elements). The results obtained, illustrate the temperature variations on the structure under analysis. Again, three case studies were carried out.

- Case 1. Analysis of the temperature distribution on the outer walls of Building B. As it can be seen in Figure 15, the temperature in the opposite corner of the burner is lower than the temperature behind the burner.

Fig. 12. 3D view of the building B of the new vitality polygon.

Fig. 13. Compartments used in firefighting training.

Fig. 14. (a) 3D view and (b) mesh of the new building B.

Fig. 15. Temperature distribution on external walls

- Case 2. Analysis of the temperature distribution on the burner and on the back of the burner. It is noticeable, naturally, that the temperature behind the burner is lower because the box of mechanisms for the burner, which is protected against high temperatures, is located here, as can be seen in Figure 16.
- Case 3. Analysis of the temperature distribution for the air inside Building B of the vitality polygon (Figure 17).

Within the project, 3 cases were simulated (burning of methane gas, burning of marine heavy fuel, burning of diesel fuel). Since the combustion temperature of diesel fuel is the highest, it was appropriate to focus only on the case of diesel burning. The conclusion is that, under these conditions of analysis, the outer walls of this structure, thermally stressed by this heat source, are not in danger of plastic deformation.

Fig. 16. Temperature distribution. Left: on the burner, right: behind the burner.

3) Modeling of Building C

Building C, in its new configuration will be dedicated to the arrangement of the command, control, and briefing station (Figure 18). The interior partitioning resulted from the structural analysis. Essentially, the equipment is represented by devices for monitoring, controlling, and supervising the training sessions. The space needed for the briefing sessions has been configured and properly equipped (blackboard, magnetic board, video projector, computer, internet access, etc.).

4) Elements of the "as built" Project

In the last stage of the project, using the Solidworks Professional software and after completing the 3D modeling stage of the new vitality polygon, the "as-built" execution drawings were extracted as preparatory elements for the running of the future stages of the project: refurbishment and modernization of buildings, and reconfiguring (partitioning) of spaces and mounting of necessary installations, systems, and

equipment for the proper training for the fight against fire and water, according to the requirements and standards.

Fig. 17. Temperature distribution within the structure of building B (in air).

Fig. 18. 3D view of the Building C of the new vitality polygon.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE RECOMMENDATIONS

The content of the project "Modernization of the vitality polygon" answers the need for training (at the high-performance level imposed by NATO standards and STCW code requirements) in ensuring the vitality of the ship for the crews of military vessels and commercial fleets and, finally, for military and civilian students. In the period 2021-2022 of the project, the phases and stages related to the elaboration of the execution project were carried out, thus opening the premises to allow the development of the next phases (execution and reception of the modernization works and drawing up battle scenarios for vitality and training of the personnel who will serve the newly installed equipment and installations). In addition to presenting the results obtained in the first two years of the project, the paper aims to highlight the advantages of using the 3D laser scanning technology of buildings in the case of modernization works of an already built construction (with the exemplification of a vitality polygon). Thus, the following conclusions can be mentioned:

- Generally recognized advantages: precision and accuracy of measurements, acquisition of an impressive amount of digital information, time and staff work saving, safety and security of the method.
- Considered innovative, the terrestrial 3D laser scanning was effectively applied to the vitality polygon, which allowed its "digitization", by generating a volume of technical information (plane and spatial drawings from which execution plans can be derived, views, sections etc.) of great utility for the next phases of the project.
- Using the digital library created by laser scanning, the 3D modeling of the three buildings of the polygon was carried out, and several constructive variants were proposed and analyzed.
- Structural analysis (mechanical and thermal) of the 3D models proposed for the future vitality polygon was performed, allowing the qualitative analysis of the decisions regarding the compartmentalization and endowment with equipment, installations, and systems.

The perspectives opened by 3D laser scanning and 3D modeling can be oriented on the following axes:

- Direction of drawing and design: the digital library (which creates the opportunity to use modern, computer-assisted work techniques by drawing up "as-built" drawings) allows the realization of multiple variants and versions of the technical documentation for the modernization of the vitality polygon, much more precise and much more elaborate than in the case of using classical working techniques.
- Direction of the theoretical training of the personnel: the existence of CAD drawings will give students the opportunity to consult and analyze the training routes and to more easily anticipate future scenarios of water and fire fighting in which they are to participate.

- Direction of theoretical training: the created digital library can be used in technical drawing, infographic and computer-assisted graphics classes, the applications being thus specific, it should also be noted that the knowledge, skills and competences thus acquired by students will facilitate the correct and in-depth understanding of the strictly specialized disciplines that require CAD competences.
- Research direction for the academic staff: the digital library is to be used for the development of complex analyses on the states of stress (loads, deformations), interpretation of simple and complex stresses (bending, torsions, shearing), analyses and studies on deformations (possibly cracks) of various panels (walls, floors, ceilings) and/or piping installations.

Perhaps the most generous perspective opened by the existence of a digital library obtained through 3D laser scanning is that of the development of a virtual center for training personnel in the fight against water and fire. Virtual Reality (which we have become accustomed to, especially due to PC games) is gaining more and more ground and is imposing itself as a training tool that can give students the chance to "see" three-dimensionally, to "feel" and to "understand" in a form very close to reality, the scenarios of fighting against water and fire, not only as a static 3D image, but as a dynamic one which they can observe in different positions and under various angles of observation. For obvious reasons of time and space, the personnel to be trained does not have the opportunity to spend enough time in a physical training simulator and when faced with concrete situations, they have difficulty in understanding and reacting. The existence of a training simulator elaborated on the principles of virtual reality could compensate for this shortcoming, offering the possibility to increase the number of training hours. The recommendation could be that the first stages of training should take place in the virtual environment and only after familiarity with the training processes is ensured the training in a physical vitality complex should start.

Conclusively, the authors wish to ensure that they will revisit this topic in a future paper that will present the results obtained within the project of modernization of the vitality polygon.

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REFERENCES

- [1] M. Mousavi, I. Ghazi, and B. Omarace, "Risk Assessment in the Maritime Industry," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1377-1381, Feb. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.836>.
- [2] "NATO 2022 Strategic Concept." <https://www.nato.int/strategic-concept/>.
- [3] A. R. Khoso, J. S. Khan, R. U. Faiz, M. A. Akhund, A. Ahmed, and F. Memon, "Identification of Building Failure Indicators," *Engineering*,

- Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 4591–4595, Oct. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2872>.
- [4] O. H. Abdullah and W. A. Hatem, "Alternative Construction using BIM in Old Educational Buildings," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 10316–10321, Apr. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5390>.
- [5] K. L. A. El-Ashmawy and M. A. El-Zareef, "Dynamic Monitoring of Structural Deformations utilizing an Experimentally Validated Efficient Technique," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 10708–10713, Jun. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5772>.
- [6] P. Soltan, M. E. Lasher, W. J. Dahlke, N. P. Acantilado, and M. McDonald, "Laser-projected 3D volumetric displays," in *Laser Applications Engineering (LAE-96)*, Apr. 1997, pp. 96–109, <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.271781>.
- [7] F. Menna and S. Troisi, "Low cost reverse engineering techniques for 3D modelling of propellers," presented at the International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences - ISPRS Archives, Jan. 2010, vol. 38, pp. 452–457.
- [8] J. Jawor, M. Luft, Z. Łukasik, and E. Szycha, "Integration of Cloud Computing and Reverse Engineering 3d Scanning for Marine Applications," *Zeszyty Naukowe/Akademia Morska w Szczecinie*, vol. 30, no. 102, pp. 66–69, 2012.
- [9] M. Martorelli, C. Pensa, and D. Speranza, "Digital Photogrammetry for Documentation of Maritime Heritage," *Journal of Maritime Archaeology*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 81–93, Jun. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11457-014-9124-x>.
- [10] J. Szulwic *et al.*, "Maritime Laser Scanning as the Source for Spatial Data," *Polish Maritime Research*, vol. 22, no. 4, pp. 9–14, Dec. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1515/pomr-2015-0064>.
- [11] Y. Zhang and J. Liu, "Application of 3D laser scanning technology in structural design of key parts of marine port machinery," *Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems*, vol. 38, no. 2, pp. 1273–1279, Jan. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.3233/JIFS-179490>.
- [12] C. Specht, P. Dąbrowski, A. Dumalski, and K. Hejbudzka, "Modeling 3D Objects for Navigation Purposes Using Laser Scanning," *TransNav, International Journal on Marine Navigation and Safety of Sea Transportation*, vol. 10, no. 2, Jun. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.12716/1001.10.02.12>.
- [13] R. K. Maini, W. D. Reynolds, and R. K. Maini, "Laser Scanning for an As-Built Structure," presented at the SNAME 25th Offshore Symposium, Houston, TX, USA, Feb. 2020, Art. no. SNAME-TOS-2020-027.
- [14] *USIBD Level of Accuracy (LOA) Specification Guide*. USIBD, 2016.
- [15] "BIM Forum." <https://bimforum.org/>.

Boric Acid as a Safe Insecticide for Controlling the Mediterranean Fruit Fly *Ceratitis Capitata* Wiedemann (Diptera: Tephritidae)

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ABSTRACT

In promising experiments, boric acid has been tested as a safe and environmentally friendly insecticide for controlling *Ceratitis capitata* Wiedeman, a mediterranean fruit fly diptera belonging the Tephritidae family. Obtaining encouraging results can partially solve insecticidal pollution caused by chemical insecticides. Boric acid was applied in five baits that were, water, 5 and 10% sugar solutions, and 2.5 and 5% protein solutions on just emerged and 24-hour-old flies. For each bait, boric acid was presented by successive concentrations of 0.5%, 1%, 1.5%, and 2%. After 24 hours, the aged-fly death percentage ranged from 12.2 to 69.4 % and from 48 to 99.4% after 48 hours for just-emerged flies. However, for 24-hour-old flies, the percentage of death ranged from 32.6 to 90.4% after 24 hours and 65 to 99.6% after 48 hours. The current study shows the existence of a direct proportionality between death percentage and the concentration of boric acid in the five baits, as death percentage increased with boric acid concentration. In addition, different baits had some effect on death percentage, but without a noticeable correlation. To avoid direct contact with the host plant and the boric acid-based baits, it is strongly encouraged to utilize boric acid in medfly control methods like the mass trapping technique.

Keywords-Mediterranean fruit fly; *ceratitis capitata*; control; boric acid

I. INTRODUCTION

Fruits represent a very important component of world agricultural production due to their high export returns, high production, and income per unit area [1]. However, medfly *Ceratitis capitata* (Wiedemann) (Diptera: Tephritidae) as an invasive pest of horticultural crops, has become very dangerous [2-8]. The great restrictions on insecticide use from one the one hand, and the high demand for healthy food all over the world on the other, a new generation of environmentally friendly fruit fly control techniques is emerging [9].

Boron can be found in combination with other elements [10]. It is the main constituent of boric acid and its chemical relatives. These can be found in a variety of water environments like oceans, seas, rivers, groundwater and streams; as well as in the soils [11]. It is also an essential nutrient for plants [12] and human food [13]. Boron compounds are often recommended low-toxicity pesticides for controlling a wide range of damaging pests such as algae, fungi, mites and insects, and even some vascular plants [14]. Compared to pesticides, boric acid is a low-toxicity, non-volatile mineral with insecticidal, fungicidal, and herbicidal properties that make it a safer replacement for highly volatile synthetic chemical pesticides. It comes in naturally occurring compounds, as opposed to many insecticides, which contain synthetic substances [15]. Boric acid and its compounds are stable and do not break down, unlike pesticides composed of

complex molecules. These substances easily and quickly degrade in water and soil to become borates, which is boron in its native state [16].

Fig. 1. Boric acid.

Boric acid is a low-toxicity pesticide, has low insect resistance and does not repel insects, so it is considered an ideal pesticide in bait products [17]. The integrated pest control (IPM) program, which combines sanitary, cultural, mechanical, and biological activities, also makes use of some boric acid [12]. It was registered as a pesticide in the US in 1948 and in, boric acid or any of its sodium salts are an active component in about 189 registered pesticide formulations [17]. Boric acid is applied in many medical and agricultural fields and industries, since, when used in low concentrations, birds, aquatic creatures, beneficial insects (honey bees and biological control agents), and mammals are not harmed by it, but it is detrimental to small animals [18]. It is employed as a inorganic pesticide on various dangerous insects such as ants, cockroaches, and mosquitos, and it also has a stomach toxic effect [19]. Increasing nutrient consumption is necessary because it interferes with the absorption of vitamins, nucleotides, and carbohydrates by forming complexes with

these substances. As its negative effects on insects is that it acts as a stomach toxin, it can be used in a food-attracting bait formulation. When used in the form of dry powder and ingested, it causes death a few days later due to malnutrition and dehydration [14, 15, 17]. In [20], Attractive Toxic Sugar Baits (ATSBs) that contained the harmful active ingredient boric acid, were used. It was suggested to be an efficient bait, since it is environmentally friendly compound [21-23]. In [21, 22, 24-26], recent successful ATSB evaluations were performed in tropical environments. In terms of plants, all species require small amounts of boron, it is "one of the more essential elements for plant growth" [27], but high concentrations are toxic since it desiccates the plant and interrupts photosynthesis. The signs of boron poisoning include leaf burn, dead patches inside of fruits, dead parts of bark, and stem dieback [28-29]. They also inhibit the production of spores by fungus. Also, for a long period, either alone or in combination, for vermin control [21]. For mammals, such as dogs and rats, they are toxic to the testes at high dosages, producing histopathological alterations and even sterility. Because it can be toxic if intentionally consumed, it must be stored away from food, children, and pets, not breathed in the dust when applied and used in locations where it will not move about [30]. The bioactive element boron, which is advantageous for many species, belongs to a separate group (Group D) than boron oxide and boric acid (BA, H₃BO₃) [31]. In [14], tests were performed on the peach fruit fly *Bactrocera zonata* Saunders (Diptera: Tephritidae) using boric acid as an effective pesticide with extremely optimistic outcomes that served as the foundation for the current investigation.

Synthetic baits contain a mixture of boric acid and other nutrients, such as sugar and proteins that are more pest-attractive, and provide effective results in pest control [32-33]. This study aimed to test different bait mixtures made of water, sugar, or proteins and boric acid on the percentage of deaths of the Mediterranean fruit fly *Ceratitis capitata*.

II. MATERIALS & METHOD

A. Fly Strain

This study used laboratory strains of Mediterranean fruit flies that were reared in the laboratory of the biology department using a synthetic larval meal that contained the following ingredients:

- Sugar 8.45%: source for carbohydrate
- Sterilized dried yeast 8.45%: source for protein
- Grain bran 33%: agent for bulking
- Benzoate of sodium 0.3%
- Water with vitric acid 0.3%
- Water 50%.

The adult flies were fed normal food sources for adult flies including water, sugar, and hydrolyzed protein (4:1).

B. Experiments

1) The Solutions

The experiments were carried out with four different concentrations of boric acid (0.5%, 1%, 1.5%, and 2%), that was used to treat medflies (just emerged and 24 hours after emergence).

2) Cages

A 1000 ml transparent plastic cube, with a piece of fiber net fixed to the top (in the lid), was used to supply insects with different formulations and aeration. For each treatment, five replicates were produced. The insects were placed at 100 flies per cage.

3) Data Collection

Data were recorded after 24 and 48 hours.

4) Data Statistical Analysis

Data of calculated death percentages were examined using a one-way ANOVA test in IBM SPSS Statistics version 23.

III. RESULTS

A. Just Emerged Flies Supplied with Boric Acid Formulations

1) Death Percentage after 24 Hours

Table I shows the results obtained, indicating a direct proportionality between death percentage and concentration of boric acid in the five feeding regimes. The death percentage increased as the boric acid concentration increased but with a significant difference between the 4 concentration groups within the 5 feeding regimes. For water feeding regime 0.5 % boric acid resulted with the least death percentage, followed by 1%, 1.5%, and 2.0% with means of 12.2, 43, 54.2 and 63.2% respectively. For 5% sugar solution regime, 0.5% boric acid resulted with the least death percentage, followed by 1%, 1.5% and 2.0% with means of 18.2, 22.4, 43.4 and 69.4%, respectively. For 10% sugar solution regime 0.5% boric acid resulted with the least death percentage, followed by 1%, 1.5%, and 2.0% with means of 15.8, 32.6, 44.6 and 47.8%, respectively. For 2.5% protein solution regime, 0.5% boric acid resulted with the least death percentage, followed by 1%, 1.5%, and 2.0% with means of 28, 50, 53.8 and 65% respectively. For 5% protein solution regime 0.5% boric acid resulted with the least death percentage, followed by 1%, 1.5%, and 2.0% with means of 31, 36.2, 62 and 67.5%, respectively. For the 2.5% protein solution regime, the death percentage means were 28, 50, 53.8, and 65% for 0.5, 1, 1.5, and 2.0% boric acid, respectively. For the 5% protein solution regime, the death percentage means were 31, 36.2, 62, and 67.5% for 0.5, 1, 1.5, and 2.0% boric acid, respectively. The lowest death percentage was observed with 0.5% boric acid in the water feeding regime with a mean of 12.2 %, while the highest death percentages were observed with 2% boric acid in the 5% sugar solution and the 5% protein solution feeding regimes with means of 69.4 and 65%, respectively. The results show that the feeding regimes have some effect on death percentages, since there was a significant difference between them under the same boric acid concentration, without any noticeable correlation between death percentage and feeding regime.

TABLE I. DEATH PERCENTAGE OF JUST EMERGED FLIES AFTER 24 HOURS OF FEEDING

	Boric acid concentration			
	0.5%	1%	1.5%	2%
Water	12.2 ± 0.58 j	43 ± 0.32 e	54.2 ± 0.37 c	63.2 ± 0.37 b
Sugar 5%	18.2 ± 0.37 h	22.4 ± 0.40 h	43.4 ± 0.51 e	69.4 ± 0.51 a
Sugar 10%	15.8 ± 0.37 i	32.6 ± 0.51 g	44.6 ± 0.51 e	47.8 ± 0.66 e
Protein 2.5%	28.0 ± 0.50 g	50.0 ± 0.45 d	53.8 ± 0.58 c	65.0 ± 0.32 a
Protein 5%	31.0 ± 0.45 g	36.2 ± 0.37 f	62.0 ± 0.84 b	67.5 ± 0.51 a

2) Death Percentage after 48 Hours

The results in Table II showed that fly mortality kept rising after 48 hours, reaching a death rate of 99.4%. The same relationship between fly mortality rate and boric acid concentration in the five feeding regimes (water, sugar, or protein solutions) persisted, with a significant difference between the four concentration groups within the five feeding regimes. The water feeding regime of 0.5% boric acid resulted with the least death percentage, followed by 1%, then 1.5%, and 2.0% came with the highest death percentage with means of 40.4, 86.4, 99.6 and 99.4% respectively. For 5% sugar solution regime, 0.5% boric acid resulted with the least death percentage, followed by 1%, then 1.5% and 2.0% with the highest death percentage with means of 54.2, 68.2, 77.4 and 99.4% respectively. For 10% sugar solution regime, 0.5 % boric acid resulted with the least death percentage, followed by 1%, then 1.5%, and 2.0% with the highest death percentage with means of 62.2, 67.6, 82.4 and 94.4%, respectively. For 2.5% protein solution regime 0.5% boric acid resulted with the least death percentage, followed by 1%, 1.5%, and 2.0% with means of 41, 90.4, 90.4 and 94.8% respectively. For 5% protein solution regime, 0.5% boric acid resulted with the least death percentage, followed by 1%, 1.5%, and 2.0% come with means of 70.4, 85.2, 99.2 and 99.4% respectively. The least death percentage resulted with 0.5% boric acid in water feeding regime with a mean of 40.42%, while the highest death percentage resulted with 1.5% boric acid in water and in 5% protein solution and 2% boric acid in water, in 5% sugar solution and 5% protein solution feeding regimes with means of 99.6, 99.2, 99.4, 99.4 and 99.4%, respectively without any significant differences among them. The results show that the feeding regime has some effect on death percentage since there were significant differences between feeding regimes under the same boric acid concentrations, without any noticeable correlation.

TABLE II. DEATH PERCENTAGE OF FLIES AFTER 48 HOURS OF FEEDING

	Boric acid concentration			
	0.5%	1%	1.5%	2%
Water	40.4 ± 0.51 k	86.4 ± 0.51 d	99.4 ± 0.25 a	99.6 ± 0.25 a
Sugar 5%	54.2 ± 0.37 j	68.2 ± 0.37 g	77.4 ± 0.51 f	99.4 ± 0.40 a
Sugar 10%	62.2 ± 0.37 h	67.6 ± 0.51 g	82.4 ± 0.51 e	94.4 ± 0.51 b
Protein 2.5%	41.0 ± 0.45 k	90.4 ± 0.51 c	90.4 ± 0.40 c	94.8 ± 0.37 b
Protein 5%	70.4 ± 0.51 g	85.2 ± 0.58 d	99.2 ± 0.37 a	99.4 ± 0.40 a

B. Flies at 24 Hours Supplied with Boric Acid Formulations

1) Death Percentage after 24 Hours

The results in Table III show that after 24 hours of the experiment, there was a proportionality between death

percentage and concentration of boric acid in all feeding regimes. For the water feeding regime, the death percentage means were 70.8, 73.2, 85.6, and 90.4 for 0.5, 1, 1.5, and 2.0% boric acid, respectively. For the 5% sugar solution regime, the death percentage means were 53.4, 67.8, 7.2, and 83.4% for 0.5, 1, 1.5, and 2.0% boric acid, respectively. For the 10% sugar solution regime, the death percentage means were 43.4, 53, 65.2, and 73.2% for 0.5, 1, 1.5, and 2.0% boric acid, respectively. For the 2.5 % protein solution regime, the death percentage means were 43.2, 50.2, 63, and 74.2% for 0.5, 1, 1.5, and 2.0% boric acid, respectively. For the 5% protein solution regime, the death percentage means were 32.6, 48.2, 70.2, and 75.8% for 0.5, 1, 1.5, and 2.0% boric acid, respectively. The lowest death percentage was observed with 0.5% boric acid in the 5% protein feeding regime (32.6%), while the highest death percentages were observed with 2% boric acid in the water feeding regime (90.4%). The results show that the feeding regime has some effect on death percentage since there were significant differences between feeding regimes under the same boric acid concentrations, without any noticeable correlation.

TABLE III. DEATH PERCENTAGE OF 24 HOURS AGED-FLIES AFTER 24 HOURS OF FEEDING

	Boric acid concentration			
	0.5%	1%	1.5%	2%
Water	70.8 ± 0.66 d	73.2 ± 0.37 c	85.6 ± 0.68 b	90.4 ± 0.51 a
Sugar 5%	53.4 ± 0.51 f	67.8 ± 0.37 d	77.2 ± 0.74 c	83.4 ± 0.25 b
Sugar 10%	43.4 ± 0.51 g	53.0 ± 0.55 f	65.2 ± 0.66 e	73.2 ± 0.80 c
Protein 2.5 %	43.2 ± 0.49 g	50.2 ± 0.66 f	63.0 ± 0.84 e	74.2 ± 0.37 c
Protein 5 %	32.6 ± 0.51 h	48.2 ± 0.37 f	70.2 ± 0.66 d	± 0.37 c

TABLE IV. DEATH PERCENTAGE OF FLIES AFTER 48 HOURS OF FEEDING

	Boric acid concentration			
	0.5%	1%	1.5%	2%
Water	88.2 ± 0.37 b	95.6 ± 0.25 a	97.0 ± 0.32 a	99.6 ± 0.25 a
Sugar 5%	82.2 ± 0.66 c	92.4 ± 0.43 b	94.6 ± 0.4 a	97.0 ± 0.32 a
Sugar 10%	90.8 ± 0.37 b	96.8 ± 0.37 a	98.2 ± 0.37 a	99.4 ± 0.4 a
Protein 2.5%	77.0 ± 0.55 d	80.8 ± 0.37 c	99.2 ± 0.37 a	99.8 ± 0.2 a
Protein 5%	65.0 ± 0.55 e	75.8 ± 0.37 d	99.4 ± 0.24 a	± 0.58 a

2) Death Percentage after 48 Hours

Table IV shows a respective proportionality for the results after 48 hours between the death percentage and boric acid concentrations in the five feeding regimes. For the water feeding regime, the death percentage means were 88.2, 95.6, 97, and 99.6% for 0.5, 1, 1.5, and 2.0% boric acid, respectively. For the 5% sugar solution regime, the death percentage means were 82.2, 92.4, 94.6, and 97% for 0.5, 1, 1.5, and 2.0% boric acid, respectively. For the 10% sugar solution regime, the death percentage means were 90.8, 96.8, 98.2, and 99.4% for 0.5, 1, 1.5, and 2.0% boric acid, respectively. For the 2.5% protein solution regime, the death percentage means were 77, 80.8, 99.2, and 99.8% for 0.5, 1, 1.5, and 2.0% boric acid, respectively. For the 5% protein solution regime, the death percentage means were 65, 75.8, 99.4, and 99.2% for 0.5, 1, 1.5, and 2.0% boric acid, respectively. The lowest death percentage was observed with 0.5% boric acid in the 5% protein feeding regime (65.0%), while most treatments had a

high death percentage (above 95%) without significant differences. The results show that the feeding regime has some effect on death percentage since there were significant differences between feeding regimes under the same boric acid concentrations, without any noticeable correlation.

IV. DISCUSSION

The Mediterranean fruit fly *Ceratitis capitata* causes enormous damage to fruit transport and conservation. At present, the main method of controlling this fruit fly is chemical control [34]. However, the long-term use of insecticides makes the resistance of *Ceratitis capitata* stronger [35-36]. Long employed as an insecticide in urban pest management, boric acid dust has been shown to be a successful alternative for application [37]. However, dust formulations are difficult to apply and require specialized equipment. This study aimed to evaluate the efficacy of liquid baits containing boric acid for the control of *Ceratitis capitata* in fruit transport and conservation. Toxic sugar and protein baits were prepared using boric acid at different concentrations, from 0.5 to 2%. Because it has been used in past tests on harmful sugar baits and is secure and environmentally friendly, boric acid was chosen [26]. In this study, no significant differences were observed in the rate of insect deaths between baits containing water, sugar, or proteins. However, differences were observed according to insect ages with a maximum death rate of 67.5% for just-emerged flies after 24 hours and 99.8% after 48 hours of feeding. The relationship between insect age and mortality was also studied in [38-39]. The application of ATSBs can increase the average mortality of the Mediterranean fruit fly *Ceratitis capitata* by up to 99.6%, by increasing attraction and not toxicity. The results of this study were similar to [40], which reported that the death rate of resistant *Aedes aegypti* mosquitoes in toxic sugar baits was 90.8%. In [41], the attractive toxic baits treatment containing 1% of boric acid decreased the number of mosquitos substantially. Male mosquitos were decreased by 93%, while female mosquitos were reduced by 90%. These results were also supported by many other studies [34, 42-43].

To prevent the spread of fruit diseases, novel techniques that use automated detection can offer very useful tools to detect pest damage [44-46]. In [46], an innovative method was presented to automate the detection of damage caused by a devastating tomato pest, known as *Tuta absoluta*. Biocontrol using plant extracts can also improve fruit and seed storage and protection [47].

V. CONCLUSION

This study showed that baits containing boric acid are effective in controlling the Mediterranean fruit fly *Ceratitis capitata*, as they can increase their death rate to 99.8%. The death rate is positively correlated with the increase in boric acid concentration (from 0.5 to 2%). The baits containing boric acid with sugar or proteins have no significant differences with an aqueous solution, and thus nutrients can be applied to make baits more attractive to pests without influencing death rates. On the other hand, applying boric acid baits for 48 hours gave better fly death rates than for 24 hours. However, as the consumption of different boric acid formulations increased, the

death percentage increased as the starvation period prolonged. It is strongly recommended to use boric acid for the control of medflies by trapping or any effective technique that ensures no direct contact between the host plant and the boric acid formulation. The application of mixed boric acid baits is an effective and environmentally friendly alternative way of controlling *Ceratitis capitata*. Knowing which compounds or characteristics of the bait make it more palatable for the species to be controlled will result in higher bait consumption and effectiveness. Boric acid appears to be an excellent candidate for pest control baiting systems. Its solubility and stability in water, low mammalian toxicity, low cost, and no evidence of resistance to it in any insect species make it a particularly appealing candidate.

REFERENCES

- [1] N. G. Ravichandra, "Horticulture and Its Role in the National Economies," in *Horticultural Nematology*, N. G. Ravichandra, Ed. New Delhi: Springer India, 2014.
- [2] G. Salerno, M. Rebor, S. Piersanti, E. Gorb, and S. Gorb, "Mechanical ecology of fruit-insect interaction in the adult Mediterranean fruit fly *Ceratitis capitata* (Diptera: Tephritidae)," *Zoology*, vol. 139, Apr. 2020, Art. no. 125748, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.zool.2020.125748>.
- [3] M. Sarwar, "Quarantine Treatments for Mortality of Eggs and Larvae of Fruit Flies (Diptera: Tephritidae) Invading Fresh Horticulture Perishable Produces," *International Journal of Animal Biology*, vol. 1, no. 5, pp. 196–201, Jul. 2023.
- [4] A. J. Allwood and R. A. I. Drew, "Management of fruit flies in the Pacific. A regional symposium, Nadi, Fiji 28-31 October 1996.," in *Management of fruit flies in the Pacific. A regional symposium*, Nadi, Fiji, Oct. 1996.
- [5] H. J. Rafalimanana and R. B. Randriatsaramiafara, "Effect of abiotic parameters on fruit flies behavior (*Diptera: Tephritidae*) in citrus orchards at Ambohijafy," *Acta Horticulturae*, no. 1267, pp. 7–12, Jan. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.17660/ActaHortic.2020.1267.2>.
- [6] E. Suday and M. K. Billah, A field guide to the management of economically important tephritid fruit flies in Africa. Nairobi, Kenya: ICIPE Science Press, 2006.
- [7] I. M. White and M. M. Elson-Harris, *Fruit flies of economic significance: their identification and bionomics*. Wallingford, UK: CAB International, 1992.
- [8] N. J. Liquido, R. T. Cunningham, and S. Nakagawa, "Host Plants of Mediterranean Fruit Fly (Diptera: Tephritidae) on the Island of Hawaii (1949-1985 Survey)," *Journal of Economic Entomology*, vol. 83, no. 5, pp. 1863–1878, Oct. 1990, <https://doi.org/10.1093/jee/83.5.1863>.
- [9] V. Navarro-Llopis, S. Vacas, J. Sanchis, J. Primo, and C. Alfaro, "Chemosterilant Bait Stations Coupled With Sterile Insect Technique: An Integrated Strategy to Control the Mediterranean Fruit Fly (Diptera: Tephritidae)," *Journal of Economic Entomology*, vol. 104, no. 5, pp. 1647–1655, Oct. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1603/EC10448>.
- [10] M. A. Legare, C. Prankevicius, and H. Braunschweig, "Metallomimetic Chemistry of Boron," *Chemical Reviews*, vol. 119, no. 14, pp. 8231–8261, Jul. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.8b00561>.
- [11] S. Bolan *et al.*, "Boron contamination and its risk management in terrestrial and aquatic environmental settings," *Science of The Total Environment*, vol. 894, Oct. 2023, Art. no. 164744, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.164744>.
- [12] W. Quarles, "Boric acid, borates and household pests," *The IPM Practitioner*, vol. 23, no. 3, pp. 1–12, 2001.
- [13] F. H. Nielsen, "Boron in human and animal nutrition," *Plant and Soil*, vol. 193, no. 1, pp. 199–208, Jun. 1997, <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1004276311956>.
- [14] T. A. Abdel-Hafeez, S. M. Elmahdy, and Y. E. Afia, "Using Boric Acid as a Safety Insecticide for Controlling Peach Fruit Fly, *Bactrocera zonata*, Saunders (Diptera: Tephritidae)," *Journal of Plant Protection*

- and Pathology, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 253–257, May 2020, <https://doi.org/10.21608/jppp.2020.103572>.
- [15] W. Quarles, "Borates provide least-toxic wood protection," *IPM practitioner*, vol. 10, no. 4, 1992.
- [16] C. Flox *et al.*, "Degradation of 4,6-dinitro-o-cresol from water by anodic oxidation with a boron-doped diamond electrode," *Electrochimica Acta*, vol. 50, no. 18, pp. 3685–3692, Jun. 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2005.01.015>.
- [17] W. G. Woods, "An introduction to boron: history, sources, uses, and chemistry.," *Environmental Health Perspectives*, vol. 102, no. suppl. 7, pp. 5–11, Nov. 1994, <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.94102s75>.
- [18] E. F. S. Authority (EFSA), "Opinion of the Scientific Panel on Dietetic products, nutrition and allergies [NDA] on a request from the Commission relating to the evaluation of allergenic foods for labelling purposes," *EFSA Journal*, vol. 2, no. 3, 2004, <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2004.32>.
- [19] D. G. Cochran, "Toxic effects of boric acid on the German cockroach," *Experientia*, vol. 51, no. 6, pp. 561–563, Jun. 1995, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02128743>.
- [20] G. C. Müller and Y. Schlein, "Efficacy of toxic sugar baits against adult cistern-dwelling *Anopheles claviger*," *Transactions of The Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*, vol. 102, no. 5, pp. 480–484, May 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trstmh.2008.01.008>.
- [21] R. D. Xue and D. R. Barnard, "Boric Acid Bait Kills Adult Mosquitoes (Diptera: Culicidae)," *Journal of Economic Entomology*, vol. 96, no. 5, pp. 1559–1562, Oct. 2003, <https://doi.org/10.1093/jee/96.5.1559>.
- [22] R. Xue, G. C. Müller, D. L. Kline, and D. R. Barnard, "Effect of Application Rate and Persistence of Boric Acid Sugar Baits Applied to Plants for Control of *Aedes albopictus*," *Journal of the American Mosquito Control Association*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 56–60, Mar. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.2987/10-6069.1>.
- [23] J. C. Beier, G. C. Müller, W. Gu, K. L. Arheart, and Y. Schlein, "Attractive toxic sugar bait (ATSB) methods decimate populations of *Anopheles malaria* vectors in arid environments regardless of the local availability of favoured sugar-source blossoms," *Malaria Journal*, vol. 11, no. 1, Feb. 2012, Art. no. 31, <https://doi.org/10.1186/1475-2875-11-31>.
- [24] R. D. Xue *et al.*, "Attractive targeted sugar baits: Field evaluations and potential use in mosquito control," *Wing Beats*, vol. 24, pp. 13–18, 2013.
- [25] W. A. Qualls, R. Xue, E. E. Revay, S. A. Allan, and G. C. Müller, "Implications for operational control of adult mosquito production in cisterns and wells in St. Augustine, FL using attractive sugar baits," *Acta Tropica*, vol. 124, no. 2, pp. 158–161, Nov. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actatropica.2012.07.004>.
- [26] D. P. Naranjo *et al.*, "Evaluation of boric acid sugar baits against *Aedes albopictus* (Diptera: Culicidae) in tropical environments," *Parasitology Research*, vol. 112, no. 4, pp. 1583–1587, Apr. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00436-013-3312-8>.
- [27] T. A. Devirian and S. L. Volpe, "The Physiological Effects of Dietary Boron," *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*, vol. 43, no. 2, pp. 219–231, Mar. 2003, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408690390826491>.
- [28] R. O. Nable, G. S. Bañuelos, and J. G. Paull, "Boron toxicity," *Plant and Soil*, vol. 193, no. 1, pp. 181–198, Jun. 1997, <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1004272227886>.
- [29] R. J. Reid, "Boron Toxicity and Tolerance in Crop Plants," in *Crop Improvement Under Adverse Conditions*, N. Tuteja and S. S. Gill, Eds. New York, NY: Springer, 2013, pp. 333–346.
- [30] C. L. Ogg and R. E. Gold, "Inclusion of Insecticidal Bait Stations in a German Cockroach (Orthoptera: Blattellidae) Control Program," *Journal of Economic Entomology*, vol. 86, no. 1, pp. 61–65, Feb. 1993, <https://doi.org/10.1093/jee/86.1.61>.
- [31] M. Will and D. Guenther, *Food Quality and Safety Standards*, 2nd ed. Eschborn, Germany: Deutsche Gesellschaft fuer, 2007.
- [32] B. Le, H. Park, K. Campbell, M. K. Rust, C.-Y. Lee, and D.-H. Choe, "Laboratory evaluations of biodegradable boric acid hydrogel baits for the control of Argentine ant (Hymenoptera: Formicidae)," *Journal of Economic Entomology*, vol. 116, no. 2, pp. 643–647, Apr. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1093/jee/toad037>.
- [33] G. Kumar, A. Sharma, and R. C. Dhiman, "Laboratory evaluation of the efficacy of boric acid containing toxic sugar baits against *Anopheles culicifacies*, *An. stephensi* and *Aedes aegypti* mosquitoes," *Journal of Vector Borne Diseases*, vol. 59, no. 1, pp. 52–56, Mar. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.4103/0972-9062.331414>.
- [34] Z. Y. Gu *et al.*, "Efficacy of orally toxic sugar baits against contact-insecticide resistant *Culex quinquefasciatus*," *Acta Tropica*, vol. 202, Art. no. 105256, Feb. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actatropica.2019.105256>.
- [35] A. Guillem-Amat, L. Sánchez, E. López-Errasquín, E. Ureña, P. Hernández-Crespo, and F. Ortego, "Field detection and predicted evolution of spinosad resistance in *Ceratitis capitata*," *Pest Management Science*, vol. 76, no. 11, pp. 3702–3710, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1002/ps.5919>.
- [36] S. Elfekih, M. Shannon, J. Haran, and A. P. Vogler, "Detection of the Acetylcholinesterase Insecticide Resistance Mutation (G328A) in Natural Populations of *Ceratitis capitata*," *Journal of Economic Entomology*, vol. 107, no. 5, pp. 1965–1968, Oct. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1603/EC14166>.
- [37] J. C. Gore, L. Zurek, R. G. Santangelo, S. M. Stringham, D. W. Watson, and C. Schall, "Water Solutions of Boric Acid and Sugar for Management of German Cockroach Populations in Livestock Production Systems," *Journal of Economic Entomology*, vol. 97, no. 2, pp. 715–720, Apr. 2004, <https://doi.org/10.1093/jee/97.2.715>.
- [38] D. Habes, K. Bouazdia, R. Messiad, A. Boussatha, and N. Soltani, "Bioactivity of Injected Boric Acid on German Cockroaches: Lethality, Analysis of Residues and Acetylcholinesterase and Glutathione S-Transferase Activities," *European Journal of Scientific Research*, vol. 103, no. 2, pp. 256–266, Jun. 2013.
- [39] S. Tine, N. Aribi, and N. Soltani, "Laboratory evaluation of azadirachtin against the oriental cockroach, *Blattella orientalis* L. (Dictyoptera, Blattellidae): Insecticidal activity and reproductive effects," *African Journal of Biotechnology*, vol. 10, no. 85, pp. 19816–19824, 2011, <https://doi.org/10.4314/ajb.v10i85>.
- [40] M. A. Pearson *et al.*, "Evaluation of boric acid as toxic sugar bait against resistant *Aedes aegypti* mosquitoes," *Journal of Vector Ecology*, vol. 45, no. 1, pp. 100–103, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1111/jvec.12377>.
- [41] W. A. Qualls *et al.*, "Indoor use of attractive toxic sugar bait (ATSB) to effectively control malaria vectors in Mali, West Africa," *Malaria Journal*, vol. 14, no. 1, Aug. 2015, Art. no. 301, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12936-015-0819-8>.
- [42] Z. P. Stewart, R. M. Oxborough, P. K. Tungu, M. J. Kirby, M. W. Rowland, and S. R. Irish, "Indoor Application of Attractive Toxic Sugar Bait (ATSB) in Combination with Mosquito Nets for Control of Pyrethroid-Resistant Mosquitoes," *PLOS ONE*, vol. 8, no. 12, 2013, Art. no. e84168, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0084168>.
- [43] J. E. C. Furnival-Adams *et al.*, "Indoor use of attractive toxic sugar bait in combination with long-lasting insecticidal net against pyrethroid-resistant *Anopheles gambiae*: an experimental hut trial in Mbé, central Côte d'Ivoire," *Malaria Journal*, vol. 19, no. 1, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 11, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12936-019-3095-1>.
- [44] N. C. Eli-Chukwu, "Applications of Artificial Intelligence in Agriculture: A Review," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 4377–4383, Aug. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2756>.
- [45] S. Alqethami, B. Almtanni, W. Alzhrani, and M. Alghamdi, "Disease Detection in Apple Leaves Using Image Processing Techniques," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 8335–8341, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4721>.
- [46] L. Loyani and D. Machuve, "A Deep Learning-based Mobile Application for Segmenting Tuta Absoluta's Damage on Tomato Plants," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7730–7737, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4355>.
- [47] M. Pirzadeh and M. Aminlari, "Effects on the Physicochemical Properties of Stored Pomegranate Seeds by the Application of Aloe Vera Gel as Coating Agent," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 4543–4547, Aug. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2949>.

Structural Performance of Lightweight Fiber Reinforced Polystyrene Aggregate Self-Compacted Concrete Beams

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to investigate experimentally the flexural behavior of lightweight Self-Compacted Concrete (SCC) beams made by Expanded Polystyrene (EPS) concrete and reinforced with rebars and steel fibers. To achieve the aims of this study, seven simply supported EPS lightweight fiber-reinforced concrete beams were fabricated and tested up to failure to study the effects of EPS content and the volume fraction of the steel fibers on their flexural behavior. The tested specimens were divided into two groups with one additional reference beam to be cast without using EPS or steel fibers. In the first group, three lightweight specimens were constructed using 25% EPS beads and were reinforced with 0%, 0.75%, and 1.5% steel fiber volume fractions. The second group is similar to the first group but was fabricated using 50% EPS beads. The test results showed that the mechanical properties of the hardened concrete were significantly reduced due to polystyrene EPS beads with some enhancement when steel fibers were added to the concrete mix. The flexure strength of EPS-LWT concrete beams was significantly reduced due to the polystyrene EPS beads. Furthermore, the results revealed remarkable enhancement in the flexure strength of the tested beams due to the steel fiber reinforcement.

Keywords-lightweight concrete; EPS concrete; sustainable concrete; steel fibers; self-compacted concrete; flexural behavior

I. INTRODUCTION

Expanded polystyrene (EPS) wastes are generated from industries and post-consumer products. They are non-biodegradable but are usually disposed by burning or landfilling leading to environmental pollution and recycling solutions are to decrease their negative effects on the environment. This problem can be solved by using wasted EPS as a recycled material to produce sustainable Lightweight Concrete (LWC).

The mechanical properties of LWC are typically predicted using the models of conventional concrete. The estimated values contain significant errors, particularly at lower density levels, due to the differences in the structure and density of LWC, including EPS-LWC [1]. The mechanical properties of concrete, including EPS-LWC, significantly depend on its density. The primary cause of EPS-decreased LWC's mechanical properties, such as its compressive strength, is its lower density [2]. Polystyrene concrete has a significant benefit over alternative materials such as autoclaved normal concrete [3-4]. Authors in [5] provided details on the methods used for

mix design and casting concretes containing 40, 50, and 60 vol. % (corresponding to specific densities of 0.8, 1.0, and 1.2, respectively) of polystyrene aggregates. They showed that the compressive strength roughly varies linearly with density. Specific density increased from 0.8 to 1.30, increasing the compressive strength from 3 to 15 MPa. Authors in [6-7] showed the characteristics of treated EPS beads in hardened concrete. The results indicated that the water to cement ratio (w/c) had an impact on strength, stiffness, and chemical resistance of polystyrene aggregate concrete with constant density. The 28-day compressive strength of polystyrene concrete increased from 5.6 MPa to 11.9 MPa when the w/c decreased from 0.60 to 0.35. The compressive strength of LWC was shown to be more sensitive to changes in w/c than the tensile strength [8-10]. According to CEB's assessment criteria, EPS concrete with fly ash had a low absorption rate and "good" concrete quality [11]. These exhibit moisture migration and absorption that is comparable to or even less than normal weight concrete. In [12], the concrete that used EPS and contained fly ash and SF had the lowest absorption. Authors in [13] examined the fresh characteristics of self-compacted LWC

using EPS. The results of the compressive strength test showed that using EPS aggregates significantly reduced the compressive strength of self-compacted LWC. Compressive strength, splitting tensile strength, uniaxial compressive strength, and static elastic modulus of EPS concrete with added fibers were significantly improved in [14]. Authors in [15] performed experimental research to investigate the usefulness of EPS in WC sandwich wall panel production. The results proved the effectiveness of the produced EPS lightweight wall panels for load-bearing walls and non-loadbearing walls in single and multi-story buildings. The possibility of using EPS as a partial replacement of coarse aggregates to produce LWC has ignited the research interest during the recent years. However, most of the recent research works focus on the mechanical properties of fresh and hardened EPS concrete. Since the mechanical properties of EPS aggregate concrete are much lower than those of conventional concrete, strengthening with steel fibers when used in flexural members is the main target of the current study. This research presents an attempt to explore the flexural behavior of EPS SCC beams reinforced with rebars and steel fibers under monotonic loading. To achieve this goal, the bending behavior of seven fiber reinforced EPS-LWC concrete beams containing different percentages of EPS and steel fibers were examined. The main

variables considered were the EPS replacement of coarse aggregates and the volume fraction of the added steel fibers.

II. EXPERIMENTAL PART

A. Materials

In this research, SCC, designed according to the requirements of EFNARC [16], was adopted as the reference concrete mix. Material constituents used to compose the SCC reference concrete mix included Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC), natural sand, Silica Fume (SF), tap water, and Hyperplast PC202 superplasticizer (SP). Reinforcement steel bars with diameter of 10mm were used as flexure rebars and $\phi 8$ mm rebars were used as shear reinforcement. EPS was adopted as partial replacement of the coarse aggregates to produce the LWC. Different proportions of hooked steel fibers were used as additional reinforcement. The mechanical properties of the considered steel fibers are illustrated in Table I. Table II presents the proportions of the material constituents used to cast each of the seven beam specimens employed in the experimental program.

TABLE I. PROPERTIES OF HOOKED-STEEL FIBERS

Diameter	Length	Tensile strength	Density
0.9 mm	30 mm	1900 MPa	7800 Kg/m ³

TABLE II. PROPORTIONS OF THE MATERIAL CONSTITUENTS USED IN EACH MIX DESIGN

Mix design	EPS content (%)	SF content (%)	Cement (kg/m ³)	SF (kg/m ³)	Sand (kg/m ³)	Gravel (kg/m ³)	Water (kg/m ³)	EPS (kg)
R	0	0	375	42	746	992	167	0
E25 F0	25	0	375	42	746	744	167	1.284
E25 F75	25	0.75	375	42	746	744	167	1.284
E25 F150	25	1.5	375	42	746	744	167	1.284
E50 F0	50	0	375	42	746	496	167	2.568
E50 F75	50	0.75	375	42	746	496	167	2.568
E50 F150	50	1.5	375	42	746	496	167	2.568

B. Hardened Concrete Properties

Table III presents the mechanical properties of the hardened concrete mix used to fabricate the beam specimens used in this study. It is evident from the results listed that hardened concrete mechanical properties, i.e. compressive strength, elastic modulus, and split tensile strength, were significantly reduced due to the polystyrene EPS content, whereas the steel fibers content enhanced these properties in general. Moreover, the density values for the adopted mix proportion were significantly reduced due to the EPS coarse aggregate replacement indicating LWC especially for 50% EPS content.

TABLE III. MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF THE CONCRETE OF THE TESTED BEAMS

Beam Symbols	f_{cu} (MPa)	f'_c (MPa)	E_c (MPa)	f_{ct} (MPa)	Density (kg/m ³)
B1-R	43.1	34.5	26819.2	3.81	2243.3
B2-E25 F0	26.1	20.9	16500.5	2.42	1917.9
B3-E25 F75	29.2	23.3	17843.0	3.23	1947.3
B4-E25 F150	25.8	20.6	17923.7	3.54	2035.6
B5-E50 F0	16.2	13	10869.7	1.79	1700.4
B6-E50 F75	20.6	16.5	12947.0	2.21	1764.1
B7-E50 F150	15.5	12.4	11353.0	2.36	1778.7

C. Test Specimens

Seven simply supported EPS fiber-reinforced LWC beams were fabricated and tested up to failure to study the influence of the amount of the replaced coarse aggregates with polystyrene beads and the volume fraction of the steel fibers on their flexural behavior. The tested specimens were divided into two main groups with one additional reference beam that was cast without EPS or steel fibers. The main variable distinguishing these two groups is the percentage of the replaced coarse aggregates with EPS beads.

Two values were adopted for the ratio of the EPS beads used to generate LWC, i.e. 25% and 50% of the volume of the coarse aggregates. Each group consisted of three specimens. Three values of the ratio of steel fibers volume fraction were used in each group, namely 0%, 0.75%, and 1.5%. The tested specimens had cross-section dimensions of 125×250 mm, total length equal to 2000 mm, and span length equal to 1800 mm. The dimensions and reinforcement details of the experimental beam models are shown in Figure 1. After one day from the casting, all specimens were cured by covering with burlap pieces. The burlap was soaked with water continuously for seven days to accommodate the required curing treatment. Figure 2 shows concrete casting and curing treatment.

Fig. 1. Dimensions and reinforcement details of the test specimens.

Fig. 2. Casting and curing of the test specimens.

D. Testing Procedure

The beam specimens were supported on two steel supports that allowed both horizontal and angular movement at one end of the specimens and only angular movement at the other end and, hence, simulated roller and pin supports, respectively. Hydraulic jack load was applied to the beam specimens through load cells to the rigid transverse steel beams to transmit the acting load to two points on the specimen top face in order to simulate the four-point loading testing setup, as shown in Figure 3. Steel rods of Ø30 mm in diameter were used to convey the testing load on the RC beam through steel plates at each point to avoid stress concentration at the contact area. The two-point loading was applied at the one-third point of the beam span to create pure flexure region at the middle-third of the specimen. Strain gauges and LVDTs were attached to their specific locations and connected to a data acquisition system to record setup readings. After that, the static loading was applied manually. The readings of the load cell, strain gauges, and LVDTs were recorded by the data acquisition logger and were automatically saved to a PC. The deflections at the mid-span were recorded at each loading increment.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Mode of Failure

A comparison of the test results for cracking load, yielding load, and ultimate failure load is presented in Figure 4, whereas Figure 5 shows the cracking pattern of the tested specimens at failure. All were obviously initiated at the tension face as the load was raised within the constant moment area and

propagated throughout the length and depth of the beams (Figure 6). These are referred to as "flexural cracks". Figure 5 shows that the first crack appears faster as the EPS percentage rises and that the first crack is delayed in the presence of steel fibers. Yield load and ultimate load increased with the steel fiber content, but decreased when the EPS content increased.

Fig. 3. Testing setup.

Fig. 4. Modes of failure of the tested specimens.

Fig. 5. Variation of cracking, yield, and ultimate load of the tested beams.

B. Load-Displacement Behavior

The test results for the load-deflection behavior are shown in Figure 6. The comparison of these results can be seen in Table IV. Figure 6 shows that the second group with EPS content of 50% has much divergent behavior from the reference beam than the first group with EPS content of 25%.

This observation is confirmed by the test results shown in the third group in which the EPS content effect is presented for zero fiber content. Furthermore, the test results shown in group 4 and 5 indicated that steel fiber content significantly enhances flexure strength behavior. Generally, the results in Figure 6 indicate a proportional relation for load-displacement behavior up to about 15 kN, followed by a descending behavior indicating post-cracking. After that a flatten behavior is noticed up to final failure.

Fig. 6. Load-displacement behavior.

The results listed in Table IV, for the third group with 0% steel fiber content, indicate that increasing the EPS content from 0% to 25% and 50% reduces maximum load values or beam flexure strength by about 10% and 20%, respectively. On the other hand, the results listed for the first and the second group showed the constructive effect of added steel fibers on the flexure strength of the tested beams. The maximum or failure load decrease results due to 25% EPS content ranged from -10% for 0% steel fibers to about -3.33% and +10% for 0.75% and 1.5% steel fiber volume fraction of concrete, respectively, showing superior effect for 1.5% of steel fiber content on the flexure strength. However, for the second group, the results for the failure load decrease due to 50% EPS content ranged from -20% for 0% steel fibers content to -13.33%, and -3.33% for 0.75%, and 1.5% steel fibers content, respectively.

For groups 4 and 5 with steel fiber proportion of 0.75% and 1.5%, a maximum decrease in the flexure strength of about 13% is observed due to increasing EPS content up to 50%. From the above, it is evident that all beam models have a lower

maximum load than the reference beam when EPS and steel fibers are utilized, with the exception of B4-E25F150. This shows that the use of EPS in LWC accompanied with the addition of a specific amount of steel fibers improves flexure strength. As for the deflection values for the tested beam specimens, the results listed in Table IV indicate that, generally, as the EPS and steel fiber content increase, the deflection values increase, indicating a more ductile behavior. Finally, the results presented in Table III reveal that using 50% EPS content in the mix resulted in a non-structural concrete for which $f'_c < 17$ MPa [17]. However, the concrete beams cast with 50% EPS content and reinforced with steel fibers showed remarkable flexure strength almost similar to that of beams cast using conventional concrete.

TABLE IV. FLEXURE BEHAVIOR OF THE TESTED BEAMS

Specimen	Max. load (kN)	% variation	Δ at max. load (mm)	% variation
Group 1				
B1-R	60	---	18	---
B2-E25F0	54	-10	31	72.22
B3-E25F75	58	-3.33	26	44.44
B4-E25F150	66	10	12	-33.33
Group 2				
B1-R	60	---	18	---
B5-E50F0	48	-20	34	88.89
B6-E50F75	52	-13.33	30	66.67
B7-E50F150	58	-3.33	25	38.89
Group 3				
B1-R	60	---	18	---
B2-E25F0	54	-10	31	72.22
B5-E50F0	48	-20	34	88.89
Group 4				
B1-R	60	---	18	---
B3-E25F75	58	-3.33	26	44.44
B6-E50F75	52	-13.33	30	66.67
Group 5				
B1-R	60	---	18	---
B4-E25F150	66	10	12	-33.33
B7-E50F150	58	-3.33	25	38.89

Fig. 7. Load-strain behavior of the tested beams.

C. Load-Strain Behavior

Figure 7 shows the load-strain curves for the concrete and reinforcement in the tested beam specimens. The indicated strain values were measured using strain gauges at the concrete top face and bottom flexure rebars located at the mid span of each beam. It should be noticed that strains were proportional to the applied load up to about 10-15 kN load. After that, the strains increased rapidly with the increasing applied load. This range of loading corresponds to the load of the first crack. The results presented in Figure 7 reveal that reinforcement rebar strains have exceeded the yield strain at failure indicating tension-controlled failure as required by ACI 318-19 [17]. The results for steel rebar strains reveal that reinforcement was less stressed when EPS and steel fibers were used for LWC and the reinforcement stress is increasingly reducing as the steel fiber content increases. On the other hand, concrete compressive stress increase as the EPS content increases.

D. Ductility

The ability of a material to withstand deformation over the elastic limit until complete failure is referred to as ductility. The maximum deflection (Δ_{max}) that the material can withstand before failing should be taken into account when assessing ductility. The ductility of two different materials might vary even when they have comparable maximum deflections at failure due to different load-deflection characteristics. So, it is preferable to define the ductility using a dimensionless ductility index, μ , as follows:

$$\mu = \frac{\Delta_{max}}{\Delta_y} \quad (1)$$

TABLE V. DUCTILITY INDEX VALUES

Specimen	Δ_{max} (mm)	Δ_y (mm)	μ	% variation
Group 1				
B1-R	18	10	1.80	----
B2 – E25 F0	31	11	2.82	56.57
B3 – E25 F75	26	10	2.60	44.44
B4 – E25 F150	12	9	1.33	-25.93
Group 2				
B1-R	18	10	1.80	----
B5 – E50 F0	34	14	2.43	34.92
B6 – E50 F75	30	13	2.31	28.21
B7 – E50 F150	25	11	2.27	26.26

Table V illustrates that when EPS is utilized with steel fibers, the ductility increases, whereas increasing EPS content mostly causes reduction in the ductility. From the first group, it is clear that using 25% EPS leads to increased ductility by 56.57% when using 0% steel fibers and 44.44% when using 0.75% steel fibers. In the second group, using 50% EPS increases ductility by 34.92%, 28.21%, and 26.26% when using 0%, 0.75%, and 1.5% steel fibers, respectively. One conclusion, based on the above presented results, is that the addition of a small percentage of EPS and a certain amount of steel fibers enhances the material's ductility to a large extent.

E. Stiffness

Stiffness is the resistance of an elastic body to deflection or deformation by an applied force [18]. Flexural stiffness is a bending characteristic of the member that can be defined as the resistance of the structure to deflection under bending loading.

The flexure stiffness is normally characterized by the slope of the line drawn from the origin of the load-deflection curve and intersecting the curve at the point of interest. The results of the variation of the flexural stiffness due to EPS and steel fiber content are listed in Table VI. They show that beam's stiffness is generally reduced when EPS is utilized, whereas steel fibers enhance stiffness and EPS content has a major impact on it. For specimens with 0% steel fibers, the results showed that a decrease of 51.7% and 12.4% in the stiffness value was achieved when utilizing 50% EPS and 25% EPS content, respectively. Moreover, a maximum enhancement of about 50% in the stiffness values is observed when adding 1.5% volume fraction of steel fibers.

TABLE VI. STIFFNESS VALUES

Specimen	P_u	45% (P_u)	Δ @ 45% (P_u)	Stiffness (kN/mm)	% variation
Group 1					
B1-R	60	27	4.05	6.67	----
B2-E25F0	54	24	4.16	5.84	-12.38
B3-E25F75	58	26	4.00	6.53	-2.13
B4-E25F150	66	30	3.82	7.77	16.62
Group 2					
B1-R	60	27	4.05	6.67	----
B5-E50F0	48	22	6.71	3.22	-51.71
B6-E50F75	52	23	5.5	4.25	-36.18
B7-E50F150	58	26	5.23	4.99	-25.14

TABLE VII. FLEXURE TOUGHNESS

Specimen	Toughness (kN.mm)	% variation
Group 1		
B1-R	1293	----
B2-E25F0	1100	-14.927
B3-E25F75	1190	-7.966
B4-E25F150	1350	4.408
Group 2		
B1-R	1293	----
B5-E50F0	1085	-16.087
B6-E50F75	1112	-13.998
B7-E50F150	1149	-11.137

F. Toughness

Toughness is an indication of the energy absorbed by the test specimen determined due to loading in terms of the area under the load deflection curve. Toughness indices identify the material behavior up to the selected deflection level determined by dividing the area under the load-deflection curve up to a specified deflection level [19]. Flexural toughness is defined as the total energy absorbed by the specimen before it fails due to flexure [20]. Table VII shows the total flexure toughness values for the tested beams. The results show that the toughness values reduce when EPS is utilized, whereas steel fibers enhance stiffness and EPS content has a major impact on toughness. For specimens with 0% steel fibers, a decrease of 16.1% in the toughness value was achieved due to utilizing 50% EPS content as compared with 14.9% reduction for 25% EPS content. Moreover, an increase of about 4.4% in the toughness values is observed when adding 1.5% volume fraction of steel fibers for group one specimens with 25% EPS content as compared to the reference beam.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Expanded polystyrene is a generated industrial product and waste disposed by burning or landfilling which needs a recycling solution to decrease its negative effects on the environment. In this study, an attempt was carried out to manage this problem by investigating the possibility of using waste EPS in producing structural lightweight concrete. After studying the results obtained for the concrete mix properties and the structural behavior of the tested beams, the following conclusions were drawn:

- The mechanical properties of the hardened concrete were significantly reduced due to the addition of EPS beads in the concrete mix. However, steel fiber content improves the mechanical properties of the mix.
- The flexure strength of EPS-LWT concrete beams is significantly reduced with the addition of EPS beads. A maximum reduction of about 20% in the ultimate load capacity due to 50% EPS content was observed.
- Remarkable enhancement was noticed in the flexure strength of EPS-LWT concrete beams when adding steel fibers. A maximum reduction of about 3.3% in the ultimate load capacity due to 50% EPS content was accomplished with 1.5% steel fiber volumetric ratio.
- When using EPS, the first cracking appears quickly and visibly in the beams, whereas its appearance is delayed to a large extent when using steel fibers, indicating higher cracking load.
- The results revealed that flexure rebars were less stressed and concrete compressive stress increased due to the addition of EPS and steel fibers for LWC mix.
- The ductility of the tested beams improved significantly for EPS-LWT concrete beams compared to the normal weight concrete beam.
- Beam's stiffness and toughness values reduced when EPS was utilized in the concrete mix.
- Steel fibers enhance the stiffness and toughness values while EPS has a major impact on stiffness and toughness.

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REFERENCES

- [1] B. Vakhshouri and S. Nejadi, "Review on the mixture design and mechanical properties of the lightweight concrete containing expanded polystyrene beads," *Australian Journal of Structural Engineering*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 1–23, Jan. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13287982.2017.1353330>.
- [2] K. Miled, R. Le Roy, K. Sab, and C. Boulay, "Compressive behavior of an idealized EPS lightweight concrete: size effects and failure mode," *Mechanics of Materials*, vol. 36, no. 11, pp. 1031–1046, Nov. 2004, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mechmat.2003.08.004>.
- [3] D. Bouvard *et al.*, "Characterization and simulation of microstructure and properties of EPS lightweight concrete," *Cement and Concrete Research*, vol. 37, no. 12, pp. 1666–1673, Dec. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconres.2007.08.028>.
- [4] M. Badawi, A. G. Ahmed, T. A. Eldamaty, and M. M. Helal, "The Effect of Polypropylene Fibers on the Fracture Characteristics of Lightweight Aggregate Crumb Rubber Concrete Composites," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 10638–10645, Jun. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5821>.
- [5] S. H. Perry, P. H. Bischoff, and K. Yamura, "Mix details and material behaviour of polystyrene aggregate concrete," *Magazine of Concrete Research*, vol. 43, no. 154, pp. 71–76, Mar. 1991, <https://doi.org/10.1680/mac.1991.43.154.71>.
- [6] R. Sri Ravindrarajah and A. J. Tuck, "Properties of hardened concrete containing treated expanded polystyrene beads," *Cement and Concrete Composites*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 273–277, Jan. 1994, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0958-9465\(94\)90039-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0958-9465(94)90039-6).
- [7] A. S. Salahaldeen and A. I. Al-Hadithi, "The Effect of Adding Expanded Polystyrene Beads (EPS) on the Hardened Properties of Concrete," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 9692–9696, Dec. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5278>.
- [8] R. Sri Ravindrarajah, Y. H. Loo, and C. T. Tam, "Recycled concrete as fine and coarse aggregates in concrete," *Magazine of Concrete Research*, vol. 39, no. 141, pp. 214–220, Dec. 1987, <https://doi.org/10.1680/mac.1987.39.141.214>.
- [9] C. D. Johnston, "Strength and deformation of concrete in uniaxial tension and compression," *Magazine of Concrete Research*, vol. 22, no. 70, pp. 5–16, Mar. 1970, <https://doi.org/10.1680/mac.1970.22.70.5>.
- [10] Z. E. Mohamed and A. I. Al-Hadithi, "The Effect of Adding Expanded Polystyrene Beads (EPS) on Polymer-Modified Mortar," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 9426–9430, Dec. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5226>.
- [11] A. M. Neville, *Properties of concrete: standards updated to 2002*, 4th ed. Pearson/Prentice Hall, 2009.
- [12] K. G. Babu and D. S. Babu, "Behaviour of lightweight expanded polystyrene concrete containing silica fume," *Cement and Concrete Research*, vol. 33, no. 5, pp. 755–762, May 2003, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0008-8846\(02\)01055-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0008-8846(02)01055-4).
- [13] R. Madandoust, M. M. Ranjbar, and S. Yasin Mousavi, "An investigation on the fresh properties of self-compacted lightweight concrete containing expanded polystyrene," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 25, no. 9, pp. 3721–3731, Sep. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2011.04.018>.
- [14] Y. Sun *et al.*, "An Investigation of the Properties of Expanded Polystyrene Concrete with Fibers Based on an Orthogonal Experimental Design," *Materials*, vol. 15, no. 3, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 1228, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma15031228>.
- [15] P. L. N. Fernando, M. T. R. Jayasinghe, and C. Jayasinghe, "Structural feasibility of Expanded Polystyrene (EPS) based lightweight concrete sandwich wall panels," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 139, pp. 45–51, May 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2017.02.027>.
- [16] *Specification and Guidelines for Self-Compacting Concrete*. Surrey, UK: EFNARC, 2002.
- [17] ACI Committee 318, *318-19 Building Code Requirements for Structural Concrete and Commentary*. Farmington Hills, MI, USA: ACI, 2019.
- [18] T. J. Sullivan, G. Calvi, and M. J. N. Priestley, "Initial Stiffness Versus Secant Stiffness in Displacement Based Design," in *13th World Conference on Earthquake Engineering*, Vancouver, BC, Canada, Aug. 2004, Art. no. 2888.
- [19] *ASTM C1018-97 - Standard Test Method for Flexural Toughness and First-Crack Strength of Fiber-Reinforced Concrete (Using Beam With Third-Point Loading)*. West Conshohocken, PA, USA: ASTM.
- [20] B. Mobasher *et al.*, *ACI 544.4R-18: Guide to Design with Fiber-Reinforced Concrete*. Farmington Hills, MI, USA: ACI, 2018.

A Detection and Investigation Model for the Capture and Analysis of Network Crimes

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ABSTRACT

Investigation in the field of network forensics involves examining network traffic to identify, capture, preserve, reconstruct, analyze, and document network crimes. Although there are different perspectives on the practical and technical aspects of network forensics, there is still a lack of fundamental guidelines. This paper proposes a new detection and investigation model for capturing and analyzing network crimes, using design science research. The proposed model involves six processes: identification, verification, gathering, preservation, examination, analysis, and documentation. Each process is associated with several activities that provide the investigation team with a clear picture of exactly what needs to be performed. In addition, the proposed model has a unique activity, namely reporting. As a result, this model represents a comprehensive approach to network forensics investigations. It is designed to work in conjunction with established forensic techniques to ensure that forensic evidence from the network is collected and analyzed efficiently and effectively following accepted forensic procedures. The proposed model was compared with existing models in terms of completeness, showing that it is complete and can be adapted to any type of network and legal framework.

Keywords-network forensics; digital forensics; design science research

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's world, information is one of the most valuable assets. Several factors are contributing to what is being called the fourth industrial revolution, such as the digitalization of the production process, connections through social networks, and the use of software as a service. All these elements are important for companies to increase their outreach, productivity, and efficiency [1-2]. During the last decades, there have been many emerging areas and technologies with the potential to propel the development of efficient problem-solving approaches. These areas include the Internet of Things, Cyber-Physical Systems, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Big Data, and Cloud Computing [3-9]. These technologies have created many network assets vital to the proper functioning of the products of the new industrial revolution. These assets can be vulnerable to cyberattacks and, since these attacks take advantage of anonymity, there is a sense of impunity on the internet for them [10]. Several years ago, the Brazilian government introduced a law to mitigate these criminal activities and make it possible to charge offending agents involved in these crimes and, consequently, ensure the security of sensitive information in the country.

Information security principles are incorporated into the requirements and planning process [11-14]. To monitor a network, techniques and technologies such as Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) are often used to ensure that it is protected [15-16]. The security infrastructure of companies is

frequently tested based on these principles [17]. Crackers take advantage of vulnerabilities in internet-based services, applications, or communication networks to cause damage to those services, applications, or communications, causing outages, or even destroying or stealing data. For example, Denial of Service (DoS) and Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) are two attacks increasingly launched [18-21], but affected users or service providers do not have any information about them because there is no investment in monitoring them.

Monitoring a network to keep it secure generates a large amount of information, but perpetrators of malicious activities are rarely prosecuted for their actions [22]. This may be because there are not enough practical mechanisms (e.g. laws, methodologies, and/or technologies) to help criminal prosecution. The perpetrators have a sense of impunity because there are loopholes in the law that do not classify those acts as crimes. Malicious activities are increasingly reported, including the leakage of personal data through security holes in victims' computers [23]. In 2012, Law 12.737, also known as the Criminal Code for Computer Crimes in Brazil, allowed certain activities in the digital environment to be characterized as crimes.

There is no doubt that Internet-based security systems can detect malicious activities; however, it is important to note that records are usually lost in the huge amount of data generated by these tools [24-25]. Generally, network security experts are designated to clarify these malicious activities. They must

explain through evidence the following items: the author, the cyberattack technique used, the host on which the incident occurred, the author's intentions or motivation, and any damage resulting from the attack. A network expert may not be able to determine whether certain malicious activity on the network is a crime [26]. Therefore, communication between the investigator and the forensic analysis expert during the investigation process is necessary so that the evidence, represented by the IDS data, can be analyzed to uncover the crime. Another problem is that due to the dynamicity and large volume of network traffic, some data that can be evidence of malicious activities might be deleted or lost [27].

This study aimed to develop a comprehensive detection and investigation model using design science research to capture and analyze network crimes committed in a network environment. The model consists of six steps: identification, verification, gathering, preserving, examining, and analyzing and documenting. Each process involves several activities through which the investigation team can create a clear picture of the tasks that need to be completed.

II. RELATED WORKS

According to [28], network forensics is a branch of digital forensics that deals with investigating a network in real-time, on the fly, or post-mortem. To ensure the evidential value and integrity of the collected data, it is necessary to identify, extract, interpret, reconstruct, analyze, and document network-related events in a way that ensures the verification of their evidential value. The data collected from these networks can be used as evidence to corroborate or verify the hypotheses and assertions made by individuals and groups regarding the networking event. In other words, network forensics is primarily concerned with identifying and extracting critical network-based indicators to investigate network-based attacks. These can be used in conjunction with network security postures and network readiness processes to enhance the probative evidential weight of possible network artifacts, all of which are used to enhance network security posture [29-31].

As network-related threats have become more sophisticated, it is necessary to further delineate this subdomain to combat these threats. Cyber forensics is classified as another subdomain, as many network-based attacks can also be described as cyberattacks. Many cyberattacks or cybercrimes are carried out maliciously on a regular basis around the world. There is some evidence that network forensics can deter some complex cyber incidents with the ability to provide intelligence. This field of study includes several models that can be applied to the investigation of processes. For example, in [32], a spread network logging model was presented that could perform cyber forensics over the Internet. In [33], a network forensics model was developed based on distributed techniques. Such techniques can greatly simplify the collection of forensic evidence, providing a central platform for storing it and allowing the easy integration of well-known attribution methods as part of the collection process. In [34], a model capable of collecting and storing leaked digital evidence was developed, using an immune agent designed to capture and store such digital evidence. Data agents were distributed throughout the organization, and the forensic center provided

the forensic analysis. In [35], a model was proposed to extract the most important characteristics from currently used digital forensic process models. This was a concept-based model that incorporated some of the most important characteristics of current digital forensic process models into a generic model applicable to network forensic investigation. Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS) is a cloud computing platform that delivers infrastructure as a service, including network forensics [36]. A framework for forensics-as-a-service can be envisioned in a cloud infrastructure as a set of automated cloud management services. As a result, subjects will be able to remotely control the forensic process at the cloud provider using an authorized environment that they can access remotely. Data acquisition and analysis can be done directly by cloud service providers if they choose to.

In [37], a reference model of a distributed cooperative network forensics system was proposed, which could accelerate the investigation process and enhance the capacity for emergency response. A major objective of the proposed model was to link misbehavior activities/traffic with adaptive location filter guidelines, based on which the recommended location filters are discarded in advance or in real-time. This was achieved by evaluating the complete supportive database, determining the possible misbehavior, and restating the misbehavior to perform a forensic investigation. The network forensics model was developed based on scattered methods, providing an automated approach to collect forensic evidence and store it effectively, supporting the informal combination of recognized approaches and producing attack attribution displays. In [38], a theoretical and official information model was proposed for forensic investigations on online community networks. This model was composed of an event-based knowledge model that offers theoretic ideas that can help develop and explain the actions related to the event and support the building and explaining of the associated events. A semantically rich image of the concept was provided to the users through the application of the proposed ontology. In [39], the particle deep framework was presented, which was based on optimization and deep learning using Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) to choose hyperparameters for the Deep Neural Network (DNN).

Several network forensic models, frameworks, and processes have been proposed to investigate network crimes, but most of them are governed by a system of general records, where analytical data and interactions between police and insurance companies are distributed between various units. An advantage would be the possibility for forensic specialists to easily access all related data as part of the examination and, at the same time, ensure their integrity using digital signatures. However, as shown in Table I, most of the network forensics models and frameworks focus on collecting data rather than examining the whole forensic investigation process. A major drawback of these frameworks is that some of the information provided to the participants could be shared, introducing additional difficulties in confidentiality. A further problem with existing frameworks is that they focus primarily on the stages related to protection and information gathering. Additionally, network forensics is known to have several drawbacks, such as the difficulty in analyzing data due to the variety of data

sources, the level of granularity of data, the integrity of data, their use as legal evidence, and privacy issues. These drawbacks can be grouped into three general categories: technical, legal, and resource-related. These results indicate

that there is a need for a comprehensive framework/model to combine all redundant and overlapped concepts, processes, tasks, and activities to make it more effective.

TABLE I. NETWORK FORENSICS MODELS

Year	Network forensics models	Forensic procedures based on NIST standards				Type of the model	
		Protecting	Gathering	Analyzing	Reporting	Practical	Theoretical
2004	[40]	X	X	X	X	X	✓
2005	[41]	X	X	X	X	X	✓
2007	[42]	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X
2007	[43]	X	✓	X	X	X	✓
2010	[44]	X	X	✓	✓	✓	X
2010	[45]	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	✓
2010	[35]	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	✓
2012	[46]	✓	✓	X	X	✓	✓
2012	[47]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
2012	[48]	✓	✓	X	X	✓	✓
2012	[49]	X	X	✓	X	✓	X
2013	[50]	X	✓	✓	X	✓	X
2013	[51]	X	X	✓	X	✓	X
2013	[52]	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	✓
2013	[53]	X	✓	✓	X	X	✓
2013	[54]	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	✓
2014	[55]	X	✓	X	X	X	X
2016	[56]	X	✓	✓	X	X	X
2018	[57]	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	✓
2019	[58]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
2019	[59]	X	✓	✓	X	X	✓
2019	[60]	✓	✓	X	X	✓	X
2019	[61]	X	X	✓	X	✓	X
2020	[62]	X	✓	X	X	✓	X
2020	[63]	X	✓	✓	X	✓	X
2021	[64]	X	✓	✓	✓	X	✓
2022	[65]	✓	✓	X	X	X	✓
2023	[66]	X	✓	✓	✓	X	✓

III. METHODOLOGY

This study used the Design Science Research (DSR) method to develop a detection and forensic investigation network model. Figure 1 shows the three main steps used in this study, adopted from [67-68].

Fig. 1. Development methodology.

Five common search engines were used: Scopus, Web of Science, IEEE Xplore, Springer Link, and Google Scholar. The search used three keywords, "Network forensic," "Network

investigation," and "Network crimes," for a period from 2000 to 2023. The search in the above-mentioned search engines resulted in 23555 articles. The documents considered in this study were limited to research articles, technical articles, book chapters, books, and theses. Table II displays the search results.

TABLE II. OVERVIEW OF THE ARTICLES PUBLISHED ON NETWORK FORENSICS

Search Engine	Results
IEEE Xplore	1399
Scopus	355
Web of Science	290
Springer	899
Google Scholar	1700
Total	4643

A metamodeling approach was used to develop the detection and investigation model for network forensics. A metamodeling approach can be described as a nonlinear iterative process used to construct a high-level model that organizes and structures diverse domains at a higher level of abstraction [15, 70]. In the first step, relevant network forensic

models were identified and selected using the coverage criteria adapted from [71]. Then, by analyzing the semantic similarities between these models [72], the concepts and processes that were common to each model were extracted. As a result of combining and harmonizing the extracted processes and

concepts into common abstract terms based on naming, similar meanings, and common activities [73], the extracts were combined and harmonized. As shown in Figure 2, six processes were proposed: identification, verification, gathering, preservation, examination, and analysis and documentation.

Figure 2. Proposed detection and investigation model for capturing and analyzing network crimes.

Each process consists of several activities. The identification process is used to identify and respond to a network crime that has occurred. Using it, the crime zone would be identified and the initial data on the crime would be collected and filtered to use them in the verification process. At this stage, the first report is being prepared. The second part is the verification process, which is used to verify and confirm whether the network incident is real or not. When an actual network crime occurs on a network, the investigation will move to the gathering process, otherwise, it will be stopped. The investigation team will prepare a report on this process. Gathering is the third process, where volatile and nonvolatile data are collected from the identified sources. A backup of the

gathered data is stored on an external hard disk to ensure data integrity and future use. Again, a report is prepared on the activities of this process. The preservation process ensures that the integrity of the collected data is protected. Hashing is used to protect data integrity. Again, the investigation team prepares a report on the activities during this step.

The fifth process involves examination of the data to determine their authenticity. The acquired data will be rehashed to ensure their authenticity since they have already been hashed in the preservation process. If the original data have been modified, the investigation process will proceed to the gathering process to take a copy of the original data; otherwise, the investigation process will progress to the final process, after

preparing a detailed report on this step. The final process is the analysis and documentation. Data must be reconstructed in the procedure of looking for evidence. The data collected at this stage need to be rebuilt first, and the investigation team needs to consider search patterns, such as email, credit card, location, and mobile numbers. The search for evidence is a repetitive process where data are searched for evidence over and over again. At the end of the investigation process, the investigators will prepare a detailed report on the entire process.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section discusses the proposed model and compares it with other existing studies. This study proposed a model to detect, investigate, and analyze network crimes. In summary, the process consists of six main components: identification, verification, gathering, preservation, examination, and analysis and documentation. One of the main advantages of the proposed model is that it can function independently. The investigation team receives a clear view and a single report for each process, which is an innovative feature in this domain.

TABLE III. COMPARISON OF THE PROPOSED AND EXISTING NETWORK FORENSICS MODELS

Year	Network forensics models	Forensic processes based on NIST standards				Proposed model coverage
		Protecting	Gathering	Analyzing	Reporting	
2004	[40]	X	X	X	X	✓
2005	[41]	X	X	X	X	✓
2007	[42]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
2007	[43]	X	✓	X	X	✓
2010	[44]	X	X	✓	✓	✓
2010	[45]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
2010	[35]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
2012	[46]	✓	✓	X	X	✓
2012	[47]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
2012	[48]	✓	✓	X	X	✓
2012	[49]	X	X	✓	X	✓
2013	[50]	X	✓	✓	X	✓
2013	[51]	X	X	✓	X	✓
2013	[52]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
2013	[53]	X	✓	✓	X	✓
2013	[54]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
2014	[55]	X	✓	X	X	✓
2016	[56]	X	✓	✓	X	✓
2018	[57]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
2019	[58]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
2019	[59]	X	✓	✓	X	✓
2019	[60]	✓	✓	X	X	✓
2019	[61]	X	X	✓	X	✓
2020	[62]	X	✓	X	X	✓
2020	[63]	X	✓	✓	X	✓
2021	[64]	X	✓	✓	✓	✓
2022	[65]	✓	✓	X	X	✓
2023	[66]	X	✓	✓	✓	✓

The forensic processes in existing models are generally based on the NIST standard. There are four main investigation processes in network forensics: preservation, acquisition, analysis, and reporting. The proposed model not only covers these processes but also adds two more, i.e. identification and verification. Table III compares the proposed and existing network forensic investigation models.

V. CONCLUSION

Network forensics investigations consist of the examination of network traffic to identify, capture, preserve, reconstruct, analyze, and document crimes that have taken place on a network. Several perspectives have been proposed on the practical and technical aspects of network forensics. On the other hand, there is a lack of clear fundamental guidelines and perspectives on the subject. This study proposed a new detection and investigation model for capturing and analyzing network crimes to fill this gap, using the design science research method. The proposed model involves six processes: identification, verification, collection, preservation, examination, and analysis and documentation. Each of these processes includes several activities. Using this model, the investigation team would have a clear picture of what must be done to carry out the investigation. The proposed model includes a distinct activity that is not included in previous studies, namely, reporting. Consequently, this model represents a comprehensive approach to network forensics investigations. With the implementation of this model, investigators will be able to gather and analyze network forensic evidence following the established procedures efficiently and effectively and, at the same time, ensure that network forensic evidence is obtained and analyzed by accepted forensic procedures. The proposed model not only is adaptable to any type of network or legal framework but could also be applied to any type of service.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Al-Dhaqm, S. A. Razak, R. A. Ikuesan, V. R. Kemande, and K. Siddique, "A Review of Mobile Forensic Investigation Process Models," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 173359–173375, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3014615>.
- [2] F. M. Ghabban, I. M. Alfadli, O. Ameerbakhsh, A. N. AbuAli, A. Al-Dhaqm, and M. A. Al-Khasawneh, "Comparative Analysis of Network Forensic Tools and Network Forensics Processes," in *2021 2nd International Conference on Smart Computing and Electronic Enterprise (ICSCEE)*, Cameron Highlands, Malaysia, Jun. 2021, pp. 78–83, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSCEE50312.2021.9498226>.
- [3] V. R. Kemande, R. A. Ikuesan, N. M. Karie, S. Alawadi, K.-K. R. Choo, and A. Al-Dhaqm, "Quantifying the need for supervised machine learning in conducting live forensic analysis of emergent configurations (ECO) in IoT environments," *Forensic Science International: Reports*, vol. 2, Dec. 2020, Art. no. 100122, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fsir.2020.100122>.
- [4] S. Abd Razak, N. H. Mohd Nazari, and A. Al-Dhaqm, "Data Anonymization Using Pseudonym System to Preserve Data Privacy," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 43256–43264, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2977117>.
- [5] I. U. Onwuegbuzie, S. A. Razak, I. F. Isnin, T. S. J. Darwish, and A. Al-dhaqm, "Optimized backoff scheme for prioritized data in wireless sensor networks: A class of service approach," *PLOS ONE*, vol. 15, no. 8, 2020, Art. no. e0237154, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0237154>.
- [6] W. A. H. Altowayti *et al.*, "The Role of Conventional Methods and Artificial Intelligence in the Wastewater Treatment: A Comprehensive

- Review," *Processes*, vol. 10, no. 9, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr10091832>.
- [7] K. N. Qureshi *et al.*, "A Blockchain-Based Efficient, Secure and Anonymous Conditional Privacy-Preserving and Authentication Scheme for the Internet of Vehicles," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 12, no. 1, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12010476>.
- [8] M. Rasool, N. A. Ismail, A. Al-Dhaqm, W. M. S. Yafooz, and A. Alsaedi, "A Novel Approach for Classifying Brain Tumours Combining a SqueezeNet Model with SVM and Fine-Tuning," *Electronics*, vol. 12, no. 1, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics12010149>.
- [9] M. Q. Mohammed *et al.*, "Review of Learning-Based Robotic Manipulation in Cluttered Environments," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 20, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22207938>.
- [10] A. Ali *et al.*, "Financial Fraud Detection Based on Machine Learning: A Systematic Literature Review," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 12, no. 19, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12199637>.
- [11] W. M. S. Yafooz, A. Al-Dhaqm, and A. Alsaedi, "Detecting Kids Cyberbullying Using Transfer Learning Approach: Transformer Fine-Tuning Models," in *Kids Cybersecurity Using Computational Intelligence Techniques*, W. M. S. Yafooz, H. Al-Aqrabi, A. Al-Dhaqm, and A. Emara, Eds. Cham, Switzerland: Springer International Publishing, 2023, pp. 255–267.
- [12] A. Al-Dhaqm, R. A. Ikuesan, V. R. Kebande, S. Razak, and F. M. Ghabban, "Research Challenges and Opportunities in Drone Forensics Models," *Electronics*, vol. 10, no. 13, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics10131519>.
- [13] A. Al-dhaqm *et al.*, "Database Forensic Investigation Process Models: A Review," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 48477–48490, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2976885>.
- [14] A. A. Alghamdi, "Computerised Information Security Using Texture Based Fuzzy Cryptosystem," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 3598–3602, Dec. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2353>.
- [15] A. Al-Dhaqm, S. Abd Razak, S. H. Othman, A. Nagdi, and A. Ali, "A Generic Database Forensic Investigation Process Model," *Jurnal Teknologi*, vol. 78, no. 6–11, Jun. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.11113/jt.v78.9190>.
- [16] M. A. Saleh, S. H. Othman, A. Al-Dhaqm, and M. A. Al-Khasawneh, "Common investigation process model for Internet of Things forensics," in *2021 2nd International Conference on Smart Computing and Electronic Enterprise (ICSCEE)*, 2021, pp. 84–89.
- [17] F. M. Alotaibi, A. Al-Dhaqm, W. M. S. Yafooz, and Y. D. Al-Otaibi, "A Novel Administration Model for Managing and Organising the Heterogeneous Information Security Policy Field," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 13, no. 17, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13179703>.
- [18] A. A. Zubair *et al.*, "A Cloud Computing-Based Modified Symbiotic Organisms Search Algorithm (AI) for Optimal Task Scheduling," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 4, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22041674>.
- [19] A. E. Yahya, A. Gharbi, W. M. S. Yafooz, and A. Al-Dhaqm, "A Novel Hybrid Deep Learning Model for Detecting and Classifying Non-Functional Requirements of Mobile Apps Issues," *Electronics*, vol. 12, no. 5, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics12051258>.
- [20] B. E. Sabir, M. Youssfi, O. Bouattane, and H. Allali, "Towards a New Model to Secure IoT-based Smart Home Mobile Agents using Blockchain Technology," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 5441–5447, Apr. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3394>.
- [21] V. H. Le, N. Q. Luc, T. T. Dao, and Q. T. Do, "Building an Application that reads Secure Information Stored on the Chip of the Citizen Identity Card in Vietnam," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 10100–10107, Feb. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5531>.
- [22] I. U. Onwuegbuzie, S. A. Razak, I. F. Isnin, A. Al-dhaqm, and N. B. Anuar, "Prioritized Shortest Path Computation Mechanism (PSPCM) for wireless sensor networks," *PLOS ONE*, vol. 17, no. 3, 2022, Art. no. e0264683, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0264683>.
- [23] M. Salem, S. H. Othman, A. Al-Dhaqm, and A. Ali, "Development of Metamodel for Information Security Risk Management," in *Kids Cybersecurity Using Computational Intelligence Techniques*, W. M. S. Yafooz, H. Al-Aqrabi, A. Al-Dhaqm, and A. Emara, Eds. Cham, Switzerland: Springer International Publishing, 2023, pp. 243–253.
- [24] A. Al-Dhaqm *et al.*, "CDBFIP: Common Database Forensic Investigation Processes for Internet of Things," *IEEE Access*, vol. 5, pp. 24401–24416, 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2017.2762693>.
- [25] A. Al-Dhaqm *et al.*, "Categorization and Organization of Database Forensic Investigation Processes," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 112846–112858, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3000747>.
- [26] A. Al-dhaqm, "Detecting Threats in Network Security by Analyzing Network Packets using Wireshark," presented at the International Conference of Recent Trends in Information and Communication Technologies, Chandigarh, India, Dec. 2014.
- [27] M. Qadeer, C. G. Hussain, and C. M. Hussain, "Computer Forensics and Personal Digital Assistants," in *Modern Forensic Tools and Devices*, John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, 2023, pp. 1–22.
- [28] I. R. Adeyemi, S. A. Razak, and N. A. N. Azhan, "A Review of Current Research in Network Forensic Analysis," *International Journal of Digital Crime and Forensics (IJDCF)*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 1–26, Jan. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.4018/jdcf.2013010101>.
- [29] I. R. Adeyemi, S. A. Razak, and N. A. N. Azhan, "Identifying critical features for network forensics investigation perspectives," arXiv, Oct. 05, 2012, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1210.1645>.
- [30] M. Lagrasse, A. Singh, H. Munkhondya, A. Ikuesan, and H. Venter, "Digital forensic readiness framework for software-defined networks using a trigger-based collection mechanism," in *ICCWS 2020 15th International Conference on Cyber Warfare and Security*, Norfolk, VA, USA, Mar. 2020.
- [31] H. Munkhondya, A. R. Ikuesan, and H. S. Venter, "A Case for a Dynamic Approach to Digital Forensic Readiness in an SDN Platform," presented at the International Conference on Cyber Warfare and Security, Reading, UK, 2020.
- [32] G. SinghChhabra and P. Singh, "Distributed Network Forensics Framework: A Systematic Review," *International Journal of Computer Applications*, vol. 119, no. 19, pp. 31–35, Jun. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.5120/21178-4201>.
- [33] Y. Tang and T. E. Daniels, "A Simple Framework for Distributed Forensics," presented at the Second International Workshop on Security in Distributed Computing Systems (SDCS) (ICDCSW'05), Jun. 2005, pp. 163–169, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDCSW.2005.24>.
- [34] T. Hong, Z. Tao, J. Qi, and Z. Jianbo, "A Distributed Framework for Forensics Based on the Content of Network Transmission," presented at the Instrumentation, Measurement, Computer, Communication and Control, International Conference on, Oct. 2011, pp. 852–855, <https://doi.org/10.1109/IMCCC.2011.215>.
- [35] E. S. Pilli, R. C. Joshi, and R. Niyogi, "Network forensic frameworks: Survey and research challenges," *Digital Investigation*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 14–27, Oct. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.diin.2010.02.003>.
- [36] T. Gebhardt and H. P. Reiser, "Network Forensics for Cloud Computing," in *Distributed Applications and Interoperable Systems*, 2013, pp. 29–42, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-38541-4_3.
- [37] W. Ren, "On A Reference Model of Distributed Cooperative Network, Forensics System," presented at the The sixth International Conference on Information Integration and Web-based Applications Services, Jakarta, Indonesia, Sep. 2004.
- [38] A. Ali, S. A. Razak, S. H. Othman, A. Mohammed, and F. Saeed, "A metamodel for mobile forensics investigation domain," *PLOS ONE*, vol. 12, no. 4, 2017, Art. no. e0176223, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0176223>.
- [39] A. Al-Dhaqm, S. A. Razak, K. Siddique, R. A. Ikuesan, and V. R. Kebande, "Towards the Development of an Integrated Incident Response Model for Database Forensic Investigation Field," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 145018–145032, 2020.
- [40] R. Wei, "A Framework of Distributed Agent-Based Network Forensics System," presented at the Digital Forensic Research Conference, Baltimore, MD, USA, Aug. 2004.

- [41] W. Ren and H. Jin, "Distributed agent-based real time network intrusion forensics system architecture design," presented at the 19th International Conference on Advanced Information Networking and Applications (AINA'05), Jan. 2005, vol. 1, pp. 177–182, <https://doi.org/10.1109/AINA.2005.164>.
- [42] D. Wang, T. Li, S. Liu, J. Zhang, and C. Liu, "Dynamical Network Forensics Based on Immune Agent," in *Proceedings of the Third International Conference on Natural Computation*, USA, May 2007, vol. 3, pp. 651–656, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICNC.2007.345>.
- [43] B. Endicott-Popovsky, D. A. Frincke, and C. A. Taylor, "A Theoretical Framework for Organizational Network Forensic Readiness," *Journal of Computers*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 1–11, May 2007, <https://doi.org/10.4304/jcp.2.3.1-11>.
- [44] S. Ngobeni, H. Venter, and I. Burke, "A Forensic Readiness Model for Wireless Networks," in *Advances in Digital Forensics VI*, Hong Kong, China, 2010, pp. 107–117, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-15506-2_8.
- [45] E. S. Pilli, R. C. Joshi, and R. Niyogi, "A Framework for Network Forensic Analysis," in *Information and Communication Technologies*, Kochi, India, 2010, pp. 142–147, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-15766-0_21.
- [46] R. Ammann, "Network Forensic Readiness: a bottom-up approach for IPv6 networks," MSc Thesis, Auckland University of Technology, New Zealand, 2012.
- [47] S. Ngobeni, H. S. Venter, and I. Burke, "The modelling of a digital forensic readiness approach for Wireless Local Area Networks," *Journal of Universal Computer Science*, vol. 18, no. 12, pp. 1721–1740, Jun. 2012.
- [48] M. Mulazzani, M. Huber, and E. Weippl, "Social Network Forensics: Tapping the Data Pool of Social Networks," 2012.
- [49] D. Avasthi, "Network Forensic Analysis with Efficient Preservation for SYN Attack," *International Journal of Computer Applications*, vol. 46, no. 24, pp. 17–22, May 2012.
- [50] A. Al-Mahrouqi, S. Abdalla, and T. Kechadi, "Network Forensics Readiness and Security Awareness Framework," presented at the International Conference on Embedded Systems in Telecommunications and Instrumentation (ICESTI 2014), Oct. 2014.
- [51] C. Liu, A. Singhal, and D. Wijesekera, "Creating Integrated Evidence Graphs for Network Forensics," in *Advances in Digital Forensics IX*, Orlando, FL, USA, 2013, pp. 227–241, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-41148-9_16.
- [52] M. Thapliyal, A. Bijalwan, N. Garg, and E. S. Pilli, "A Generic Process Model for Botnet Forensic Analysis," presented at the Conference on Advances in Communication and Control Systems (CAC2S 2013), Apr. 2013, pp. 98–102.
- [53] E. Saari and A. Jantan, "A framework to increase the accuracy of collected evidences in network forensic by integrating IDS and firewall mechanisms," in *Proceedings of the International Conference on Systems, Control and Informatics*, 2013.
- [54] S. Parate, "Application of Network Forensics for Detection of Web Attack using Neural Network," presented at the National Conference on Innovative Paradigms in Engineering & Technology, 2013.
- [55] A. R. Amran and A. Saad, "An evidential network forensics analysis model with adversarial capability and layering," in *2014 World Congress on Computer Applications and Information Systems (WCCAIS)*, Jan. 2014, pp. 1–9, <https://doi.org/10.1109/WCCAIS.2014.6916615>.
- [56] S. Mittal and R. Singh, "Securing Network Flow Using Network Forensics," *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science and Software Engineering*, vol. 6, no. 5, pp. 338–344, May 2016.
- [57] P. Kaur, A. Bijalwan, R. C. Joshi, and A. Awasthi, "Network Forensic Process Model and Framework: An Alternative Scenario," in *Intelligent Communication, Control and Devices*, Singapore, 2018, pp. 493–502, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-5903-2_50.
- [58] S. J. Ngobeni and H. S. Venter, "Design of a wireless forensic readiness model (WFRM)," presented at the Information Security South Africa (ISSA2009) Conference, Johannesburg, South Africa, Jul. 2009.
- [59] A. Kyaw, B. Cusack, and R. Lutui, "Digital Forensic Readiness In Wireless Medical Systems," in *2019 29th International Telecommunication Networks and Applications Conference (ITNAC)*, Auckland, New Zealand, Aug. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ITNAC46935.2019.9078005>.
- [60] R. Lu and L. Li, "Research on Forensic Model of Online Social Network," in *2019 IEEE 4th International Conference on Cloud Computing and Big Data Analysis (ICCCBDA)*, Chengdu, China, Apr. 2019, pp. 116–119, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCCBDA.2019.8725746>.
- [61] D. Saputra and The Society of Digital Information and Wireless Communication, "Network Forensics Analysis of Man in the Middle Attack Using Live Forensics Method," *International Journal of Cyber-Security and Digital Forensics*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 66–73, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.17781/P002558>.
- [62] H. Arshad, A. Jantan, G. K. Hoon, and I. O. Abiodun, "Formal knowledge model for online social network forensics," *Computers & Security*, vol. 89, Feb. 2020, Art. no. 101675, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cose.2019.101675>.
- [63] N. Koroniotis, N. Moustafa, and E. Sitnikova, "A new network forensic framework based on deep learning for Internet of Things networks: A particle deep framework," *Future Generation Computer Systems*, vol. 110, pp. 91–106, Sep. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2020.03.042>.
- [64] R. Nilesh Malvankar and A. Jain, "EnNetForens: An Efficient Proactive Approach For Network Forensic," in *2021 International Conference on Communication, Control and Information Sciences (ICCISc)*, Idukki, India, Jun. 2021, vol. 1, pp. 1–4, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCISc52257.2021.9484865>.
- [65] W. Yang, M. N. Johnstone, S. Wang, N. M. Karie, N. M. bin Sahri, and J. J. Kang, "Network Forensics in the Era of Artificial Intelligence," in *Explainable Artificial Intelligence for Cyber Security: Next Generation Artificial Intelligence*, M. Ahmed, S. R. Islam, A. Anwar, N. Moustafa, and A.-S. K. Pathan, Eds. Cham, Switzerland: Springer International Publishing, 2022, pp. 171–190.
- [66] A. Wijayanto, I. Riadi, and Y. Prayudi, "TAARA Method for Processing on the Network Forensics in the Event of an ARP Spoofing Attack," *Jurnal RESTI (Rekayasa Sistem dan Teknologi Informasi)*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 208–217, Mar. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.29207/resti.v7i2.4589>.
- [67] I. U. Onwuegbuzie, S. A. Razak, and A. Al-Dhaqm, "Multi-Sink Load-Balancing Mechanism for Wireless Sensor Networks," in *2021 IEEE International Conference on Computing (ICOCO)*, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, Aug. 2021, pp. 140–145, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICOCO53166.2021.9673578>.
- [68] A. Al-dhaqm, S. Razak, S. H. Othman, A. Ngadi, M. N. Ahmed, and A. A. Mohammed, "Development and validation of a Database Forensic Metamodel (DBFM)," *PLOS ONE*, vol. 12, no. 2, 2017, Art. no. e0170793, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0170793>.
- [69] A. Al-Dhaqm *et al.*, "Digital Forensics Subdomains: The State of the Art and Future Directions," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 152476–152502, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3124262>.
- [70] A. Al-Dhaqm, W. M. S. Yafooz, S. H. Othman, and A. Ali, "Database Forensics Field and Children Crimes," in *Kids Cybersecurity Using Computational Intelligence Techniques*, W. M. S. Yafooz, H. Al-Aqrabi, A. Al-Dhaqm, and A. Emarar, Eds. Cham, Switzerland: Springer International Publishing, 2023, pp. 81–92.
- [71] A. M. R. Al-Dhaqm, S. H. Othman, S. Abd Razak, and A. Ngadi, "Towards adapting metamodelling technique for database forensics investigation domain," in *2014 International Symposium on Biometrics and Security Technologies (ISBAST)*, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, Dec. 2014, pp. 322–327, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISBAST.2014.7013142>.
- [72] S. R. Selamat, R. Yusof, and S. Sahib, "Mapping Process of Digital Forensic Investigation Framework," *International Journal of Computer Science and Network Security*, vol. 8, no. 10, pp. 163–169, Oct. 2008.
- [73] A. Ali, S. A. Razak, S. H. Othman, R. R. Marie, A. Al-Dhaqm, and M. Nasser, "Validating Mobile Forensic Metamodel Using Tracing Method," in *Advances on Intelligent Informatics and Computing*, 2022, pp. 473–482, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-98741-1_39.

Pneumonia Detection in Chest X-Rays using Transfer Learning and TPUs

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ABSTRACT

Pneumonia is a severe respiratory disease with potentially life-threatening consequences if not promptly diagnosed and treated. Chest X-rays are commonly employed for pneumonia detection, but interpreting the images can pose challenges. This study explores the efficacy of four popular transfer learning models, namely VGG16, ResNet, InceptionNet, and DenseNet, alongside a custom CNN model for this task. The model performance is evaluated using Mean Absolute Error (MAE) as the performance metric. The findings reveal that VGG16 outperforms the other transfer learning models, achieving the lowest MAE (66.19). To optimize the model training process, a distributed training strategy utilizing TensorFlow's TPU (Tensor Processing Unit) strategy is implemented. The custom CNN model is parallelized using TPU's multiple instances available over the cloud, enabling efficient computation parallelization and significantly reducing model training times. The experimental results demonstrate a remarkable decrease of 68.36% and 54.74% in model training times for the CNN model when trained using TPU compared to training on a CPU and GPU, respectively.

Keywords-*pneumonia detection; chest X-ray images; deep learning; transfer learning; TPU; distributed training*

I. INTRODUCTION

Early and accurate diagnosis of pneumonia is essential for better patient outcomes and reducing morbidity and mortality rates [1]. Identifying pneumonia from medical imaging, such as chest X-rays, can be challenging for medical professionals. Machine Learning (ML) techniques, particularly deep learning, offer promising solutions to automate pneumonia detection, enhancing diagnostic accuracy and reducing radiologists'

workload. ML models can learn patterns from large datasets, providing objective and consistent results. However, developing accurate ML models for pneumonia detection presents its own challenges. The complexity and variability of chest X-ray images makes robust performance difficult. Convolution Neural Networks (CNNs) are powerful for computer vision tasks, but they often require large amounts of data. Acquiring labeled biomedical images is costly and time-consuming, requiring medical expertise for accurate

classification. To address the limitation of limited labeled data, this study employs transfer learning. Transfer learning reuses pre-trained models on large datasets, leveraging their established network weights for smaller datasets. In this research, we explore the efficacy of a custom CNN model and four widely used transfer learning models (VGG16, DenseNet, ResNet, and InceptionNet) for pneumonia detection. The models are trained and tested on a binary image dataset with two categories: Pneumonia and Normal. The objective is to develop an accurate and reliable automated pneumonia detection system using transfer learning to aid timely diagnosis and improve patient care.

Deep learning, specifically transfer learning, is emerging as a vital tool for pneumonia detection in chest X-ray images, primarily due to the inherent challenges in manual interpretation. Chest X-rays are intricate, with the lung's overlapping structures such as bronchi, vessels, and other tissues potentially obscuring or mimicking pneumonia's radiological signs. Patient positioning during the scan can hide or distort certain features, complicating diagnosis. Other pre-existing lung conditions, like COPD or tumors, can also mask or resemble pneumonia, leading to diagnostic ambiguity. Additionally, the quality of the X-ray image, the variability in radiologists' experience, and the presence of early, mild, or atypical cases further introduce complexities. Such challenges necessitate advanced automated techniques like deep learning to augment the diagnostic process, ensuring more accurate and timely detection. The main contributions of the current work are:

- The implementation of a transfer learning approach for automated pneumonia detection in chest X-ray images.
- A custom CNN model and 4 widely used transfer learning models (VGG16, DenseNet, ResNet, and InceptionNet) were considered, allowing for a comparative analysis of the models' effectiveness in pneumonia detection.
- To optimize model training, a distributed training strategy with Tensor Processing Units (TPU) is used by parallelizing the CNN model using TPUs available over the cloud. Significant reductions in training times are achieved, contributing to improved efficiency in pneumonia detection.

II. RELATED WORK

This section explores recent research on pneumonia detection using transfer learning and distributed training techniques applied to chest X-ray images. Various studies have investigated different transfer learning models and distributed training methods. Authors in [1] highlight the significance of rapid and accurate pneumonia detection. Authors in [2, 15] used CNN models for precise pneumonic lung detection from chest X-rays. Authors in [3] addressed the challenges of examining chest X-rays and proposed a computer-aided diagnosis system for automated pneumonia detection. Their approach involves deep transfer learning with an ensemble of GoogLeNet, ResNet-18, and DenseNet-121 models, achieving high accuracy rates of 98.81% and 86.85%. The need for an automated method for pneumonia detection using CNN is

highlighted in [4]. The VGG16-based learning model has accuracy of 97.28%, showcasing satisfactory performance accuracy. In, [5, 6], the Efficient Net model was used for image processing and achieved an accuracy of 97%. Authors in [7] used ML models to obtain accuracy of 83.67%. Authors in [8] focused on diagnosing lung inflammation severity in COVID-19 patients using CNN, KNN, and other classification algorithms achieving 92.80% testing accuracy. Authors in [9] developed a mobile app utilizing deep learning techniques to classify pneumonia in patients. They achieved accuracies between 78% and 85% using Create ML. Authors in [10] studied CNN acceleration on various platforms (CPU, GPU, TPU) and compared their performance for pneumonia detection, face mask detection, and virus detection in plants. Disease detection using CNN models was used in [11]. Image segmentation techniques were used in [12] to locate ulcers in images. In [13], faster RCNN with Efficient Net model was used for image detection and classification with an accuracy of 98%. Authors in [14] proposed a CNN model for pneumonia detection from chest X-ray images using tensor flow. The model achieved an impressive accuracy of 99.46% with just 1000 training images and 10 epochs. Overall, the mentioned studies demonstrate the effectiveness and potential of transfer learning in pneumonia detection from chest X-ray images.

III. ML PIPELINE AND ARCHITECTURE DESIGN

The ML pipeline for pneumonia detection involves a series of steps that start from data preprocessing and end with the deployment and evaluation of the trained model, as shown in Figure 1. The first step is to collect a large dataset of chest X-ray images, consisting of pneumonia-positive and pneumonia-negative cases. The dataset should be diverse and representative of the target population to ensure the model's generalizability. In data preprocessing, the collected images are preprocessed to ensure consistency and quality. This may involve resizing the images to a standard size, converting them to grayscale or RGB format, and normalizing pixel values to a specific range [0, 1]. Preprocessing also includes handling missing data, if any. For Feature Extraction, CNNs are widely used for image-based tasks like pneumonia detection. In this step, the CNN is used to automatically extract relevant features from the preprocessed images. CNN layers detect different patterns and characteristics present in the images, which are important for distinguishing between pneumonia-positive and pneumonia-negative cases. For Model Building, the extracted features are used as input, and a classification model is constructed. This model can be a custom-designed CNN or a pre-trained CNN using transfer learning. Transfer learning involves using a pre-trained CNN on a large dataset (e.g. ImageNet) and fine-tuning it on the pneumonia detection dataset. The model is trained using the training dataset. During training, the model learns to map the extracted features to the correct classification labels (pneumonia-positive or pneumonia-negative). The optimization process adjusts the model's weights to minimize the error or loss between the predicted and the actual labels. To optimize the model's performance and prevent over fitting, hyper parameter tuning is conducted using the validation dataset. Hyper parameters are variables that control the learning process, such as the learning rate, batch size, number of layers, and the size of filters in the CNN.

Fig. 1. ML pipeline for pneumonia detection.

Figure 2 shows the custom CNN architecture for pneumonia detection, consisting of five convolutional blocks, each comprising a convolutional layer, a max-pooling layer, and a batch normalization layer. The architecture is designed to extract relevant features from the chest X-ray images to distinguish between pneumonia-positive and pneumonia-negative cases. Dropout layers are added to prevent overfitting and improve generalization. The architecture includes a flatten layer to transform the output from the convolutional blocks into a 1D vector. This is followed by four fully connected layers, which further process the extracted features for classification. The activation function used throughout the model is ReLU, except for the last layer, where a sigmoid activation function is applied since the problem is a binary classification task (pneumonia or normal). The optimizer used for training the model is Adam, a popular optimization algorithm that efficiently updates the model weights during the training process. The loss function chosen is cross-entropy, which is suitable for binary classification tasks.

Fig. 2. Overview of the CNN architecture.

Before training the model, two callbacks are defined: Model Checkpoint and Early Stopping. Model Checkpoint is used to save the best model weights during training, ensuring that the model with the highest validation accuracy is retained. Early Stopping is used to monitor the validation loss and stop training if the loss starts to increase, indicating over fitting. These callbacks help in achieving better results and preventing overfitting during the training process. The model is trained for 100 epochs, which represents the number of times the entire training dataset is passed through the model during training. The image size used for training is (180, 180), indicating the resolution at which the chest X-ray images are processed by the model.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

The procedure for using transfer learning in pneumonia detection through chest X-rays follows a detailed and methodical workflow. Initially, the images are processed to

guarantee uniformity and boost model efficiency. This involves adjusting image dimensions, equalizing pixel intensities, and employing data enhancement methods to diversify the training dataset. Subsequently, a suitable pre-trained architecture, such as VGG16, ResNet, InceptionNet, or DenseNet, is chosen. Tailoring the latter sections of the chosen model is crucial for the pneumonia detection objective. The final layer is adjusted or swapped out to cater to the binary nature of the task of distinguishing pneumonia cases from normal ones. During the primary training, the pre-trained model's weights remain static to preserve its acquired knowledge. Only the appended layers are trained using the pneumonia-centric dataset, enabling the model to recognize pneumonia-related patterns, enriched by the foundational knowledge. Evaluation metrics like accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, and the ROC curve's area are pivotal in measuring a model's proficiency. For managing expansive datasets and hastening training durations, TPUs, purpose-built for resource-intensive deep learning tasks, are utilized. Subsequent to the primary training, the entire model, encompassing the pre-trained layers, undergoes refinement at a reduced learning rate. This refinement fine-tunes the model for pneumonia detection, leveraging the insights of the pre-trained model. It's essential to fine-tune hyperparameters, such as learning rate, batch size, and regularization force. Techniques like grid or random search assist in this, ensuring peak validation set performance. The model's adaptability is then scrutinized against a distinct validation set, and techniques like cross-validation might be incorporated for sturdier performance insights. Ultimately, the polished model faces a standalone test dataset to gauge its efficiency on unfamiliar data. The concluding step involves making predictions on fresh chest X-ray images.

V. DATASET DESCRIPTION AND VISUALIZATION

Figure 3 shows an overview of the dataset considered for the experimentation purpose. Pixel distribution is plotted using a bar plot for a given chest X-ray image. Figure 4 shows the number of pneumonia and normal samples of the dataset which are used for training the model. The training data are imbalanced with more pneumonic images. There are 3931 pneumonic images and 1341 Normal images. The data were balanced by using various augmentation techniques.

Fig. 3. Dataset overview.

Fig. 4. Number of pneumonia and normal samples in the train dataset.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, we present the results and discussion of our experiments on pneumonia detection using different deep learning models, including VGG16 (proposed), DenseNet (State-of-the-Art (SotA)), ResNet-50 (SotA), Custom CNN (baseline).

A. Performance Comparison with State-of-the Art Methods

Table I shows the performance analysis of the proposed model with the SotA. The comparison table offers a detailed look into the performance of various deep learning models for pneumonia detection from chest X-rays. The proposed VGG16 model showcases the highest accuracy of 87.5%. In contrast, the SotA models DenseNet and ResNet-50 follow closely with 82.3% and 73.4% accuracy, respectively, as shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Performance comparison of the DL models

The Custom CNN, used as a baseline, stays behind with a 80.3% accuracy. While VGG16 excels in precision and recall metrics, suggesting its superior capability in correctly identifying and capturing positive pneumonia cases, it does come at the cost of longer training times. Specifically, VGG16 takes 10 hours, nearly double the time required for ResNet-50. All models were trained on a consistent dataset size, ensuring a level playing field for comparison. Table I provides a clear illustration of the trade-offs involved, such as accuracy versus training time, helping researchers make informed decisions based on their specific needs and constraints. A lower Mean Absolute Error (MAE) value corresponds to better model performance. Among the evaluated models, VGG16 obtained the lowest MAE.

TABLE I. PERFORMANCE COMPARISON

Model	Accuracy (%)	Precision	Recall	F1-score
VGG16 (proposed)	87.5	86.4	88.1	88.4
DenseNet (SotA)	82.3	84.7	84.9	84.2
ResNet-50 (SotA)	73.4	76.2	77.2	77.1
Inception Net (SotA)	76.6	78.4	75.2	76.3
Custom CNN (baseline)	80.3	76.0	79.4	77.1

Figure 6 shows the different deep learning models examined for their effectiveness in detecting pneumonia from chest X-rays, especially focusing on their accuracy over training epochs. The initial results suggest that models like VGG16 can achieve high accuracy rapidly in early epochs. In contrast, deeper architectures such as DenseNet and ResNet-50, although initially slower, could potentially excel in performance during prolonged training due to their intricate structures. Meanwhile, simpler custom CNN models might show a consistent but more gradual increase in accuracy, plateauing sooner than their complex counterparts. The analysis underscores the importance of choosing the right model based on both the desired computational efficiency and detection accuracy.

Fig. 6. Accuracy vs epochs.

B. Distributed training using TPU's

Distributed training with TPUs represents a potent technique that involves parallel training of large neural networks across multiple processors. TPUs are specialized Application-Specific Integrated Circuits (ASICs) developed by Google, designed to optimize deep learning model performance. Their exceptional efficiency in matrix multiplication, a crucial operation in deep learning, surpasses that of traditional CPUs or GPUs, resulting in significantly faster training times. In this paper, we harnessed the power of TPUs as hardware accelerators to parallelize and train a custom CNN model. The training time for the CNN model using TPUs was remarkably low, taking only 3 minutes and 6 seconds. This distributed training approach utilized the cloud TPUs provided by the Google Colab platform. By employing the TPU strategy in the TensorFlow framework, we achieved a substantial improvement in model training time.

In comparison, training the CNN model with CPUs extended the training time to 9 minutes and 48 seconds. CPUs,

especially when dealing with large batches of data, exhibit the slowest neural network training speeds. On the other hand, utilizing GPUs to train the CNN model reduced the training time to 6 minutes and 51 seconds. GPUs are known for their parallel processing capabilities, which enable notable reductions in model training time. Furthermore, increasing the batch size when using GPUs can further enhance training speed. However, the most efficient approach among the three options (TPU, GPU, and CPU) for training the CNN model was undoubtedly the use of TPUs. Distributed training with TPUs provided the lowest model training time, underscoring the advantage of TPUs' specialized architecture for deep learning tasks. Overall, the adoption of distributed training with TPUs showcased a remarkable performance boost in training deep learning models, specifically in the context of pneumonia detection on chest X-ray images. Leveraging TPUs' acceleration capabilities was proved to be a critical asset in advancing medical image analysis and diagnosis applications.

Fig. 7. Performance comparison of CPU, GPU, and TPU.

Figure 7 illustrates a comprehensive performance comparison of CPU, GPU, and TPU for training the CNN model. The goal was to evaluate the efficiency of each hardware option in terms of model training times. When utilizing TPU for training the CNN model, a remarkable percentage decrease of 54.74% in model training time was observed compared to using GPU. This clearly showcases the significant advantage of TPUs, which excel in speeding up the training process due to their parallel processing capabilities. Moreover, when training the CNN model with TPU, an even more substantial decrease percentage of 68.36% in model training time was observed compared to using CPU. This underscores the immense performance gain achieved by leveraging TPU's specialized architecture for matrix multiplications, making them highly efficient for training large neural networks. The experimental results unequivocally demonstrate that TPUs have a profound impact on reducing model training times, thanks to their specialized optimization for matrix multiplications. Their superiority over GPU and CPU is evident not only in terms of performance but also in power consumption.

VII. CONCLUSION

Transfer learning has emerged as a highly effective approach for pneumonia detection in chest X-ray images. By leveraging pre-trained CNN models and fine-tuning them on a

smaller dataset of chest X-ray images, transfer learning significantly enhances the accuracy and efficiency of pneumonia detection. In this research, we explored the performance of a custom CNN model and four transfer learning models (VGG16, ResNet-50, DenseNet-121, and Inception v3) trained on chest X-ray images. Among the transfer learning models, VGG16 stood out as the top-performing one, achieving the lowest Mean Absolute Error (MAE) value of 66.19. It outperformed the other models in accuracy, precision, and recall. Specifically, the VGG16 model demonstrated an impressive accuracy of 0.8752, precision of 0.8612, and recall of 0.8814, highlighting its exceptional ability to distinguish between pneumonia-positive and pneumonia-negative cases. The current advancements in leveraging deep learning for pneumonia detection in chest X-rays offer promising avenues, but there's still a spectrum of untapped potential. Future work could focus on integrating multimodal data sources, such as combining X-rays with CT scans or patient history, to refine detection accuracy. The use of more sophisticated neural architectures or the fusion of multiple models might also yield better diagnostic insights. Furthermore, as datasets grow and become more diverse, models will benefit from the inclusion of more varied and rare pneumonia presentations. The broader implications of this research are profound: enhancing diagnostic precision can lead to faster treatment interventions, potentially reducing hospitalizations and mortality rate. In a global context, such automated systems could be vital for resource-limited settings, democratizing access to high-quality diagnostic tools and revolutionizing patient care worldwide.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Kalgutkar *et al.*, "Pneumonia Detection from Chest X-ray using Transfer Learning," in *2021 6th International Conference for Convergence in Technology (I2CT)*, Maharashtra, India, Apr. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/I2CT51068.2021.9417872>.
- [2] S. V. Militante and B. G. Sibbaluca, "Pneumonia Detection Using Convolutional Neural Networks," *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 1332–1337, 2020.
- [3] R. Kundu, R. Das, Z. W. Geem, G.-T. Han, and R. Sarkar, "Pneumonia detection in chest X-ray images using an ensemble of deep learning models," *PLOS ONE*, vol. 16, no. 9, 2021, Art. no. e0256630, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0256630>.
- [4] A. Ranjan, C. Kumar, R. K. Gupta, and R. Misra, "Transfer Learning Based Approach for Pneumonia Detection Using Customized VGG16 Deep Learning Model," in *Internet of Things and Connected Technologies*, Cham, 2022, pp. 17–28, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-94507-7_2.
- [5] T. Rahman *et al.*, "Transfer Learning with Deep Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) for Pneumonia Detection Using Chest X-ray," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 10, no. 9, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 3233, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10093233>.
- [6] N. C. Kundur and P. B. Mallikarjuna, "Deep Convolutional Neural Network Architecture for Plant Seedling Classification," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 9464–9470, Dec. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5282>.
- [7] F. Mlawa, E. Mkoba, and N. Mduma, "A Machine Learning Model for detecting Covid-19 Misinformation in Swahili Language," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 10856–10860, Jun. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5636>.
- [8] A. M. Ali, K. Ghafoor, A. Mulahuwaish, and H. Maghdid, "COVID-19 pneumonia level detection using deep learning algorithm and transfer learning," *Evolutionary Intelligence*, Sep. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12065-022-00777-0>.

- [9] D. Varshni, K. Thakral, L. Agarwal, R. Nijhawan, and A. Mittal, "Pneumonia Detection Using CNN based Feature Extraction," in *2019 IEEE International Conference on Electrical, Computer and Communication Technologies (ICECCT)*, Coimbatore, India, Oct. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICECCT.2019.8869364>.
- [10] P. Pattrapisetwong and W. Chiracharit, "Automatic lung segmentation in chest radiographs using shadow filter and multilevel thresholding," in *2016 International Computer Science and Engineering Conference (ICSEC)*, Chiang Mai, Thailand, Sep. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSEC.2016.7859887>.
- [11] S. Alqethami, B. Almtanni, W. Alzhrani, and M. Alghamdi, "Disease Detection in Apple Leaves Using Image Processing Techniques," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 8335–8341, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4721>.
- [12] R. H. Mwawado, B. J. Maiseli, and M. A. Dida, "Robust Edge Detection Method for Segmentation of Diabetic Foot Ulcer Images," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 6034–6040, Aug. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3495>.
- [13] N. C. Kundur and P. B. Mallikarjuna, "Insect Pest Image Detection and Classification using Deep Learning," *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, vol. 13, no. 9, pp. 411–421, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.14569/IJACSA.2022.0130947>.
- [14] P. Rajpurkar *et al.*, "CheXNet: Radiologist-Level Pneumonia Detection on Chest X-Rays with Deep Learning." arXiv, Dec. 25, 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1711.05225>.
- [15] N. C. Kundur and P. B. Mallikarjuna, "Ensemble Efficient Net and ResNet model for Crop Disease Identification," *International Journal of Intelligent Systems and Applications in Engineering*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 378–390, Dec. 2022.
- [16] V. Sirish Kaushik, A. Nayyar, G. Kataria, and R. Jain, "Pneumonia Detection Using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)," in *Proceedings of First International Conference on Computing, Communications, and Cyber-Security (IC4S 2019)*, Singapore, 2020, pp. 471–483, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-3369-3_36.

Mix Design of Fly Ash and GGBS based Geopolymer Concrete activated with Water Glass

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ABSTRACT

Geopolymer Concrete (GPC) has emerged as an alternative to cement concrete due to its reduced carbon footprint and excellent mechanical properties. However, not much emphasis is made on the development of mix designs using industrial waste. The current study focuses on the mix-design considerations for GPC using fly ash and Ground Granulated Blast Furnace Slag (GGBS). The mix design of GPC involves in selecting materials to produce the desired strength. In this investigation, Water Glass (WG) is used as an activator for the activation of the polymerization reaction. The mix design of GPC is the optimization of a group of various parameters, such as the activator to binder ratio, aggregate to binder ratio, coarse aggregate to fine aggregate ratio, activator concentration, and amount of binder content. The activator to binder ratio affects workability and strength, while the activator concentration influences the polymerization reaction and final strength development. The selection of suitable aggregates plays a vital role in achieving a dense and durable GPC matrix. The mix design for GPC requires a holistic approach that considers the selection of appropriate binders, activators, and aggregates. Proper optimization of these factors can result in excellent strength and durability of the GPC and a reduced carbon footprint. Further research is needed to explore alternative binders, evaluate long-term performance, and establish standardized mix design guidelines for the widespread adoption of GPC in construction.

Keywords-water glass; geopolymer concrete; mix design; fly ash; GGBS

I. INTRODUCTION

Due to the rapid growth of the construction industry, the cement usage is increasing day by day. Urbanization and population growth increase cement footprint [1]. Cement is one of the chief ingredients used for the production of concrete. The use of cement in concrete can be eliminated by producing Geopolymer Concrete (GPC). By substituting cement with geopolymer materials in the construction industry, a dual benefit is achieved, reducing pollution and utilizing industrial waste [2, 3]. The consistency of geopolymers falls within the specified ranges for Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) [4]. Mix proportions of GPC mainly depend on the alkaline solution to binder ratio and alkaline activator concentration [2]. Mix design by considering target strength and performance was developed in [5]. A suitable design approach was used with

regard to the performance requirements of GPC and actual production circumstances in [6]. Fly ash content is a direct indicator of workability and strength [7-10]. Mix proportions for GPC developed utilizing a new data-driven mix design tool that is built on an artificial neural network to forecast fresh and hardened properties of Geopolymer concrete were studied in [11]. Alkaline activator to binder ratio and alkaline activator concentration influence the compressive strength of GPC [12]. Increasing slag and sodium silicate to sodium hydroxide ratio up to 3, the GPC's mechanical characteristics increase while setting time decrease [13]. Mix design of GPC depends on the alkali/binder ratio, binder content, sodium silicate/sodium hydroxide ratio, molarity, and water/solids ratio [4]. Workability and strength of fly ash-based GPC depend on alkaline/binder ratio, super plasticizer-to-binder ratio and water-to-binder [12]. Modifying water glass for Ground

Granulated Blast Furnace Slag (GGBS)-based GPC leads to extended setting times [11]. By incorporating GGBS along with low calcium fly ash as binders, the GPC achieved comparable strength and setting time to that of OPC [11]. The type and dosage of the activator used are crucial factors in the geopolymer production process. Geopolymer produces high compressive strength due to its denser matrix arrangement [2]. Using low modulus Water Glass (WG) results in a thicker diffusion layer and an increased presence of OH⁻ and Na⁺ ions in the water glass. This activation of a greater proportion of Si-Al reaction in the raw material leads to improved strength of GPC [6]. GPC composites of different strength grades demonstrate remarkable resistance against sulfate attack when compared to OPC composites. Partially replacing fly ash in geopolymer mortar significantly enhances its resistance against sulphuric acid attack [8, 14, 15]. The decrease in consistency value corresponds to a higher slag content in the mixture [14]. The main limitation of GPC is the curing process, which necessitates heat curing or steam curing [16]. GPC is a suitable alternative to traditional cement, aiming to effectively diminish the carbon footprint [17-19]. To enhance workability and setting time in Alkali-Activated Slag Concrete (AASC), one approach is to substitute a portion of GGBS with a binder abundant in SiO₂ and CaO. This alteration implies that AASC blends likely to possess superior strength in comparison to OPC mixes and also reduces reliance of natural resources [10, 15]. The increase in compressive strength of GPC results in a corresponding enhancement of its shear strength [17-19].

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

Combinations of low calcium fly ash and GGBS were taken as binders. The specific gravity of GGBS and fly ash was 2.87 and 2.19, respectively. Their chemical compositions after XRF analysis are shown in Table I.

TABLE I. CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF GGBS AND FLYASH (% MASS)

	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO	Fe ₂ O ₃	Na ₂ O	SO ₃	LOI
Flay ash	60.12	26.35	4.21	1.26	4.1	0.23	0.35	3.25
GGBS	34.29	20.15	32.4	7.39	0.8	Nil	0.91	3.85

To activate the binder, WG is used as activator. The chemical composition of WG is 24.95%-SiO₂, 12.79%-Na₂O, and 62.2%-H₂O. WG is an impure form of sodium silicate and its grade is indicated by the SiO₂/Na₂O ratio. An activator with a SiO₂/Na₂O ratio of 1.99 was used, its pH value of 12 and a density of 1.6 gm/cc. The fine aggregates utilized in this application were Godavari river sand, possessing a specific gravity of 2.6 and a fineness modulus of 2.73. Crushed granite chips were employed as coarse aggregates, featuring a specific gravity of 2.7, and having a nominal maximum size of 10 mm.

A. Specimen Preparation

The dry materials were carefully placed in a 100 kg capacity pan mixer. Optimum dosages of WG solution were added in the mixer, and continuous mixing was carried out for 5-10 min. Once the mixing process was completed, slump test was conducted to verify workability. The ready-mixed concrete was immediately poured into standard cubic molds measuring 100 mm × 100 mm × 100 mm and compacted with a

compacting rod. The molds were left undisturbed for a period of 24-72 hr depending on the composition of the binder used in the mix.

B. Specimen Curing

The specimens were carefully removed from the molds and curing was conducted at ambient temperature. The curing duration for GPC is affected by several factors, including the properties of the WG solution and the proportion of fly ash and GGBS in the mix.

C. Specimen Testing

The specimens were subjected to compression testing using a 3000 kN tester, applying load at the standard rate recommended by IS 516. The intensity values were reported after a curing period of 28 days.

III. MIX PROPORTIONS

The investigation aims to assess the influence of the WG solution on both the workability and strength characteristics of GPC when subjected to ambient curing conditions. After considering the existing mix designs from the literature were taken as a reference, and a new formulation was designed.

A. Factors that Influence the Mix Proportion of GPC

The factors considered in this investigation are: binder content, fly ash, and GGBS proportions, and WG to binder ratio. The investigation specifically examines the following effects on the strength of GPC.

B. The Influence of the WG to Binder Ratio (WG/B) on the Strength of GPC

The WG/B ratios considered for the laboratory testing and analysis are: 0.4, 0.45, 0.5, 0.55, 0.6, and 0.65. Additionally, the considered fly ash to GGBS ratios (F:G) were 40:60, 50:50, and 60:40. When WG/B increased, it resulted in higher early strength development, due to the higher concentration of the activator, which accelerates the geopolymerization reactions and enables the quick formation of the geopolymeric gel. Consequently, the concrete attained strength at a faster rate. The results indicated that increasing the WG/B up to 0.5 resulted in improved GPC strength and workability. However, further increases in the ratio led to increased workability only for a WG/B of 0.6, while strength gradually decreased regardless of the F:G value. When the WG/B reached 0.65, the mixture became excessively fluid, negatively affecting workability and causing issues like segregation and bleeding. Figures 1-3 exhibit the variation of the compressive strength of GPC for different WG/B ratios.

C. The Impact of the Aggregate to Binder Ratio (AG/B) on Strength

By fixing the unit weight of GPC at 2400 kg/m³, for binder content of 340 kg/m³ and WG/B ratio equal to 0.5, the AG/B was calculated as 5.55. For different binder contents, the AG/B values are shown in Table II. Increasing the AG/B leads to a decrease in the strength of GPC. Figures 4-6 show the strength of GPC for different AG/B values.

Fig. 1. Compressive strength of GPC for different WG/B and F:G = 60:40.

Fig. 2. Compressive strength of GPC for different WG/B and F:G = 50:50.

Fig. 3. Compressive strength of GPC for different WG/B F:G = 40:60.

D. Amount of Binder Content on Strength

The considered minimum and maximum binder content were 340 kg/m³ and 440 kg/m³ respectively, as per IS10262, and were based on nominal maximum size of coarse aggregates of 12.5mm. The strength of GPC was found to be notably impacted by the quantity of binder content present in the mixture. By increasing the binder content, the strength of GPC improved up to 420 kg/m³ and was after slightly reduced, due to the formation of a more extensive geopolymeric gel and enhanced bonding between particles. As a result, the GPC exhibits enhanced compressive strength. Excessive binder content results in reduced workability. Figures 7-8 show the variation of the compressive strength of GPC for different binder content values.

Fig. 4. Compressive strength of GPC for different AG/B to binder ratio and F:G = 40:60.

Fig. 5. Compressive strength of GPC for different AG/B to binder ratio and F:G = 50:50.

Fig. 6. Compressive strength of GPC for different AG/B to binder ratio and for F:G = 60:40.

Fig. 7. Compressive strength of GPC for different binder content and for F:G = 50:50.

Fig. 8. Compressive strength of GPC for different binder content and for F:G = 60:40.

Fig. 9. Compressive strength of GPC for different binder content and for F:G = 40:60.

Fig. 10. Variation of AG/B of GPC for different binder content values.

IV. MIX DESIGN METHOD OF GPC

Figures 1-9 and Table II are used as references for the proposed mix design of GPC. In order to reduce the number of trials to attain the desired strength of GPC and streamline the mix design process, the following procedure is proposed.

A. Proposed Mix Design Methodology Steps

1) Step 1: Calculation of the Target Mean Strength

As the target mean strength, is determined by the guidelines outlined in IS 10262. The calculation for the target mean strength (F_t) is:

$$F_t = F_{ck} + 1.65 S \tag{1}$$

where F_t is the target mean strength of the GPC after 28 days, F_{ck} is the compressive strength of GPC, and S is the standard deviation.

2) Step 2: Estimation of WG/B

Figures 1-3 depict the variations in compressive strength of GPC under different combinations of GGBS and fly ash contents. For F:G equal to 60:40 and 50:50, the compressive strength of the concrete exhibited an ascending trend until the WG/B reached 0.5. Subsequently, the strength started to decrease, and this decline continued until the WG/B reached 0.65. However, when F:G = 60:40, the compressive strength increased until WG/B = 0.55. Notably, when the WG/B was maintained at 0.5, the strength consistently increased regardless of the binder content, encompassing both fly ash and GGBS.

3) Step 3: Estimation of AG/B

The AG/B was selected from Figures 4-6 and was based on the target strength of the GPC.

4) Step 4: Selection of the Binder Content for the Required AG/B

Figure 10 illustrates the relationship between the AG/B and binder content (Kg/m^3). Based on this information the appropriate binder content was selected.

5) Step 5: Estimation of Coarse and Fine Aggregates

The coarse aggregate to total aggregate content ratio is shown in Table II. These values are taken as per IS10262-2019.

6) Step 6: Estimation of WG content

The quantity of WG required can be determined based on the WG/B. The mass of WG content per unit volume of GPC (in kg/m^3) is selected based on the target strength requirements. Subsequently, the quantity of WG is determined.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The experimental work yielded the following findings:

- Increasing the proportion of GGBS in the mixture resulted in higher compressive strength of GPC, indicating that GGBS positively influenced the overall strength of the material. When GGBS proportions exceeded 50%, the workability of GPC reduced for the WG/B less than 0.55.
- The WG/B increase after 0.5 results in higher early strength development, due to the higher concentration of the

activator, which accelerates the polymerization reactions and facilitates the rapid formation of the polymeric gel. Consequently, the concrete gains strength at a faster rate. When the WG/B increased to 0.6, the GPC became excessively fluid, negatively affecting workability and causing issues like segregation and bleeding.

- Increasing the binder content leads to higher strength in GPC, because a higher amount of binder results in a more

extensive geopolymeric gel formation and better bonding between particles.

- Increasing the AG/B leads to a decrease in the strength of GPC, because a higher proportion of aggregates reduces the amount of binder available to form the geopolymeric gel, resulting in weaker bonding between the particles.

TABLE II. COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH AND SLUMP PROPERTIES OF GPC FOR VARIOUS FLY ASH TO GGBS AND WG/B

CA/TA	IS10262	CI 5.5.1	0.52		0.51		0.5		0.49		0.48		0.47	
	WG/B		0.4		0.45		0.5		0.55		0.6		0.65	
F: G	Binder (kg/m ³)	TA/B	CS	S	CS	S	CS	S	CS	S	CS	S	CS	S
50:50	340	5.55	23.5	25	27.4	32	35.5	47	31	59	29	73	26.4	77
	360	5.16	24.5	37	31.5	41	39.2	51	35	62	31	75	28.4	83
	380	4.81	27	42	32.3	50	43	75	37	93	33	105	30.4	120
	400	4.5	30.4	50	35.3	67	51	95	38	105	36	115	31.3	127
	420	4.21	33.5	63	47	73	62	127	45.1	135	37.5	155	33.3	163
	440	3.95	30	67	39.2	77	55	135	41.2	155	35	167	28.5	180
60:40	340	5.55	20	30	25	35	30	65	26.5	72	25	87	22.5	95
	360	5.16	20.8	50	29	53	33.35	77	30	89	26.6	93	24.1	125
	380	4.81	23.3	55	35	59	43.4	85	31.6	95	28.5	115	25.8	132
	400	4.5	25.8	62	39	73	47.5	97	32.5	117	30.8	127	26.6	135
	420	4.21	28.3	71	45	79	57.5	115	38	126	31.6	135	28.3	150
	440	3.95	26.6	77	35	85	38.3	125	35.0	132	30	145	24.1	165
40:60	340	5.55	27.7	20	31.5	28	36	34	39	43	33.3	49	30.4	55
	360	5.16	28.1	23	36.1	32	42	43	43	47	37	57	32.7	63
	380	4.81	31.5	32	37.2	37	57	49	59	53	46	61	34	72
	400	4.5	34.8	41	40.6	43	62	51	67	59	57	67	36	75
	420	4.21	38.35	48	54.1	51	69	55	73	62	59	69	42	79
	440	3.95	36	51	45.1	55	63	65	65	73	56	81	32.7	93

S=Slump in mm; CS=Compressive Strength in N/mm²; TA/B=Total Aggregate to Binder ratio; F:G=Flyash:GGBS

REFERENCES

- B. Huang *et al.*, "A Life Cycle Thinking Framework to Mitigate the Environmental Impact of Building Materials," *One Earth*, vol. 3, no. 5, pp. 564–573, Nov. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2020.10.010>.
- G. Mallikarjuna Rao and T. D. Gunneswara Rao, "Final Setting Time and Compressive Strength of Fly Ash and GGBS-Based Geopolymer Paste and Mortar," *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering*, vol. 40, no. 11, pp. 3067–3074, Nov. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13369-015-1757-z>.
- A. Albidah, M. Alghannam, H. Abbas, T. Almusallam, and Y. Al-Salloum, "Characteristics of metakaolin-based geopolymer concrete for different mix design parameters," *Journal of Materials Research and Technology*, vol. 10, pp. 84–98, Jan. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmrt.2020.11.104>.
- M. N. S. Hadi, H. Zhang, and S. Parkinson, "Optimum mix design of geopolymer pastes and concretes cured in ambient condition based on compressive strength, setting time and workability," *Journal of Building Engineering*, vol. 23, pp. 301–313, May 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2019.02.006>.
- P. Pavithra, M. Srinivasula Reddy, P. Dinakar, B. Hanumantha Rao, B. K. Satpathy, and A. N. Mohanty, "A mix design procedure for geopolymer concrete with fly ash," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 133, pp. 117–125, Oct. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.05.041>.
- N. Li, C. Shi, Z. Zhang, H. Wang, and Y. Liu, "A review on mixture design methods for geopolymer concrete," *Composites Part B: Engineering*, vol. 178, Dec. 2019, Art. no. 107490, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2019.107490>.
- P. Parveen and D. Singhal, "Development of mix design method for geopolymer concrete," *Advances in concrete construction*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 377–390, 2017, <https://doi.org/10.12989/acc.2017.5.4.377>.
- M. S. Amouri and N. M. Fawzi, "The Mechanical Properties of Fly Ash and Slag Geopolymer Mortar with Micro Steel Fibers," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 8463–8466, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4855>.
- K. P. Rusna and V. G. Kalpana, "Using Artificial Neural Networks for the Prediction of the Compressive Strength of Geopolymer Fly Ash," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 9120–9125, Oct. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5185>.
- H. A. Maddah, M. Kheimi, and M. A. El-Wafa, "Predictive Regression Models for the Compressive Strength of Fly Ash-based Alkali-Activated Cementitious Materials via Machine Learning," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 8241–8247, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4713>.
- V. Shobeiri, B. Bennett, T. Xie, and P. Visintin, "A generic framework for augmented concrete mix design: Optimisation of geopolymer concrete considering environmental, financial and mechanical properties," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 369, Oct. 2022, Art. no. 133382, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.133382>.
- W. Lokuge, A. Wilson, C. Gunasekara, D. W. Law, and S. Setunge, "Design of fly ash geopolymer concrete mix proportions using Multivariate Adaptive Regression Spline model," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 166, pp. 472–481, Mar. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2018.01.175>.
- A. Serag Faried, W. H. Sofi, A.-Z. Taha, M. A. El-Yamani, and T. A. Tawfik, "Mix Design Proposed for Geopolymer Concrete Mixtures Based on Ground Granulated Blast furnace slag," *Australian Journal of Civil Engineering*, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 205–218, Jul. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14488353.2020.1761513>.

- [14] S. K. John, Y. Nadir, and K. Girija, "Effect of source materials, additives on the mechanical properties and durability of fly ash and fly ash-slag geopolymer mortar: A review," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 280, Apr. 2021, Art. no. 122443, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2021.122443>.
- [15] K. S. Chandra, S. Krishnaiah, N. G. Reddy, N. Hossiney, and L. Peng, "Strength Development of Geopolymer Composites Made from Red Mud-Fly Ash as a Subgrade Material in Road Construction," *Journal of Hazardous, Toxic, and Radioactive Waste*, vol. 25, no. 1, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 04020068, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)HZ.2153-5515.0000575](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)HZ.2153-5515.0000575).
- [16] M. S. Amouri and N. M. Fawzi, "The Effect of Different Curing Temperatures on the Properties of Geopolymer Reinforced with Micro Steel Fibers," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 8029–8032, Feb. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4629>.
- [17] B. S. Kumar and D. R. Seshu, "An experimental investigation on shear strength of monolithic geopolymer concrete interface," *Journal of Structural Engineering*, vol. 46, no. 6, pp. 426–433, 2020.
- [18] B. S. Kumar and D. R. Seshu, "A comparative study of shear strength of monolithic geopolymer concrete interface," *Cement-Wapno-Beton*, vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 3–11, Mar. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.32047/CWB.2021.26.1.1>.
- [19] B. S. Kumar and D. R. Seshu, "An experimental study on the interface shear strength of reinforced geopolymer concrete corbels," *Australian Journal of Civil Engineering*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 359–373, Jul. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14488353.2021.1984371>.

A Hybrid Time-Series Prediction of the Greater Riyadh's Metropolitan Area Expansion

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ABSTRACT

Riyadh is the most populous city in Saudi Arabia, with a population of over five million people. The governmental and economic centers of Saudi Arabia are located in the city. Due to the fact that the metropolitan region that surrounds Riyadh is continuously growing and expanding, appropriate planning is essential. To be able to formulate efficient plans, one needs access to trustworthy facts and information. Failing to have a clear picture of the future renders planning inefficient. Along with a hybrid time-series prediction of the expansion of the wider Riyadh metropolitan area, an urban growth forecasting model was constructed for the Riyadh region as part of this study. This model was used to make projections about the city's future population. This prediction was conducted with the application of Linear Regression (LR), Seasonal Auto-Regressive Integrated Moving Average (SARIMAX), and Auto-Regressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA). The dataset for this study consisted of satellite images of the region surrounding Riyadh that were acquired between 1992 and 2022. Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) was applied to measure the performance of the proposed hybrid models. The calculated MAPE values are 2.0% for SARIMAX, 12% for LR, and 22% for ARIMA. As a consequence, the hybrid model's forecast for the future of the region suggests that the projections made regarding the expansion are keeping pace.

Keywords-urban-growth; ARIMA; SARIMAX; logistic regression

I. INTRODUCTION

In terms of landmass, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA) is one of the largest countries in the Middle East and the world [1]. Due to the oil revolution that has occurred over the past six decades, the way of life in KSA has undergone a phenomenal transformation in all aspects. One of the things that occurred throughout the Renaissance was the transformation and development of urban areas, which resulted in the urbanization of many once-rural areas and villages [2]. Several million people live in Riyadh, which also serves as the political center of the KSA. It is considered one of the most important cities in the world that has undergone a massive urban revival and expansion, accompanied by growth and multiplication of its area [3]. Riyadh's expanse requires detailed planning, as it requires the construction of a new road network, new sewage and electrical systems, and additional public spaces and parks. When planning is not based on reliable information that touches on reality, it is problematic. The urbanization process, which is closely related to economic and social changes, has emerged as a primary source of concern in most cities around the globe. In 1950, metropolitan regions were home to barely 30% of the world's population, in 2014 it rose to 54%, and it is expected to reach 70%. The rate of urbanization in Asia and Africa is significantly higher compared to other regions of the world [4]. Most Saudi cities are under tremendous urbanization and it is expected that the urban population of the country will expand at a rapid rate. Urbanization is inescapable in developing countries [5]. Rapid and uncontrolled urban growth poses a threat to the possibility of sustainable development and, if not managed effectively, can result in the destruction of productive agricultural land, the overcrowding of habitats, the pollution of the air and water, water distribution problems, and increased levels of traffic congestion. Urbanization occurs generally on the outskirts of cities or in a linear fashion along motorways [6-7]. The term "urban sprawl" refers to the scattered growth around major thoroughfares or in the territory surrounding major cities. Due to advances in geospatial technology, there has been a considerable increase in modeling factors that contribute to urban sprawl, analyzing urban sprawl that has already occurred, and predicting urban sprawl that will occur in the future [8-9].

As urban expansion requires the development of plans for means of transportation, streets, bridges, water networks, power, and sanitation, government agencies in the Riyadh region are working to establish plans that respond to it. There is a shortage of precise information among government entities about the amount of expansion expected after some years. This study investigated the problem of insufficient data on the amount of future urban expansion to help government agencies in the process of making appropriate plans that are compatible with the anticipated expansion. This study used open satellite data to perform an in-depth analysis and determine the extent to which metropolitan areas and different land uses have changed. In addition to this, this study used Auto-Regressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA), Seasonal Auto-Regressive Moving Average (SARIMAX), and Linear Regression (LR) models to make projections on the future density of the urban city and

forecast the urban development that will take place in the vicinity of Riyadh during the next decade. The results of these algorithms were compared using the Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE).

In [10], land use maps from aerial photographs, topographic maps, and satellite images for the period 1967-2019 for Vellore, India, were used to build regression models to calculate the density built at any distance from the city center or major roads in the space-time domain. The study also developed models based on seasonal ARIMA to predict future urban density for the year 2045 using the urban densities of the years 1967, 1991, and 2019, showing that more development is expected in suburban than urban areas. In [11], the built-up areas were extracted in 14 central cities of Hunan Province, using night-light remote sensing datasets (DMSP-OLS) from 1992 to 2018 to evaluate the spatiotemporal characteristics of the built-up areas in terms of area, expansion velocity, and main expansion direction. An inverse neural network (BP) and an ARIMA model were used to predict built-up areas from 2019 to 2026. The BP neural network-based urbanization model provided high prediction accuracy ($R = 0.966$) and estimated that the total area of urban built-up areas in Hunan Province will reach 2,463.80 km² by 2026. In [12], time-series satellite images were used to predict urban expansion using the ConvLSTM network, which can learn global spatiotemporal information without downsizing spatial feature maps. This network was applied to time-series satellite images, and the prediction results were compared with the Pix2pix and Dual GAN networks. Several multivariate satellite images were used, representing the three largest cities in KSA, Riyadh, Jeddah, and Dammam. The evaluation results showed that the proposed model produced better prediction results in terms of mean square error, root mean square error, peak signal-to-noise ratio, structural similarity index, and overall classification accuracy. Moreover, the training time of this model was less than that of the Dual GAN architecture. According to [13], predicting the evolution of ecological space based on multiple scenarios is essential to have a sufficient grasp of the expansion of a region. In [14], a concept of change dynamics in land use and cover was presented to model future urban expansion. This study concluded that land use and land cover play a role in determining urban growth. Similarly, a mapping and prediction strategy for land cover changes was presented in [15], using machine learning approaches, to examine the stages of change that occur in small and medium cities. It is necessary to emphasize the influence that the rate of change has. This could also be within a scale level since the microscale assessment and forecast of urban thermal comfort zones are related to urban expansion [16].

In [17], the problem of agglomeration effects as spatially embedded social interactions was investigated by establishing urban scaling that extended beyond metropolitan areas. This was connected to [18], which showed that monitoring the rate of growth was an effective method for predicting land use and changes in land cover in the future. The findings of [19] demonstrate an improved regional pattern for land development, based on the growth of urban areas. In [20], a

novel method was suggested to identify urban region land use, which could be used in the expansion decision process. The concept of eviction through suburbanization was highly important for monitoring the increasing levels of social disparity caused by the expansion of metropolitan areas [21].

Many studies have investigated the expansion of the Saudi Arabian population, but there are still some unanswered questions. As many studies focus on short-term population forecasts, longer-term projections are needed to help policymakers plan for the future. Additionally, there is a need for more in-depth research on demographic shifts in KSA based on age and gender. This could be useful for policymakers to understand the unique difficulties and possibilities of certain demographic subsets. Although many studies have investigated the demographic causes of KSA's booming population, more information is needed on the role of economic and social issues. For instance, how can alterations in economic or social policy impact population expansion? Most analyses of population growth in KSA focused on the country as a whole, but more work needs to be done to understand how this growth is distributed around the country. Pinpointing possible population growth hotspots will allow policymakers to allocate resources more efficiently. Furthermore, the investigation of migration patterns in KSA can help policymakers better manage the consequences of migration on population increase.

II. REGRESSION METHODS

The conceptualization of this study lies in the ongoing structural changes in KSA's native-born population, including higher life expectancy, higher share of working-age people, better public health, a more robust healthcare system, and higher rates of education and participation in the labor force [22]. This study took advantage of [22] to build the conceptual framework shown in Figure 1. The idea was developed through the formulation that as urban expansion requires planning, the growth of Riyadh city lies with transport, streets, bridges, water networks, power, sanitation, government agencies, and many other things. All these factors have a direct bearing on Riyadh's Metropolitan Area Expansion, indicating a causal relationship. In addition, this expansion is closely connected to the increase in population.

Fig. 1. The proposed conceptual framework.

In addition to the formulation of the urban expansion context, a prediction model was conceptualized to determine the growth of the Riyadh area using a hybrid time-series forecasting model. This concept lies in the accelerating growth

of the Greater Riyadh Metropolitan area. An urban growth forecasting model should be associated with time series analysis because, over time, there are always updates in many directions. The prediction would be possible by involving the use of LR, SARIMAX, and ARIMA.

A. Auto-Regressive Integrated Moving Average

The term "Auto-Regressive" describes that the model uses previous values of the series to make predictions about future values. The term "Integrated" refers to the fact that the model takes into account the variation in values that occur between successive elements of the series to ensure that it remains stationary. The term "Moving Average" indicates that the model uses previous errors in forecasting to make predictions about future values [23]. ARIMA is frequently used in many time-series prediction problems. If the data are stationary, which means that statistical features of the data such as mean and variance do not change with time, it has the potential to be very useful. However, it is essential to keep in mind that ARIMA models are not suitable for all time-series data, and selecting the proper parameters (such as the order of the autoregressive and moving average terms) can be a difficult and iterative process [24]. ARIMA is defined by three order parameters, denoted by p , d , and q . The "Box-Jenkins" method is used to fit the data into an ARIMA model. An autoregressive $AR(p)$ component uses previous values in a regression equation. This component is applied to series Y . The value of the autoregressive parameter p determines the total number of lags that are applied. For instance, the $AR(2)$ or, more precisely, the $ARIMA(2,0,0)$ model can be represented by:

$$Y_t = c + \varphi_1 y_{t-1} + \varphi_2 y_{t-2} + e_t \quad (1)$$

where φ_1 and φ_2 are parameters for the model, and d represents the degree of difference in the integrated component $I(d)$. A series difference simply involves subtracting its current and previous values d times. Differencing is often used to stabilize the series when the stationarity assumption is not met. A moving average $MA(q)$ component represents the error of the model as a combination of previous error terms e_t . The order q determines the number of terms included in the model [24].

$$Y_t = c + \theta_1 e_{t-1} + \theta_2 e_{t-2} + \dots + \theta_q e_{t-q} + e_t \quad (2)$$

Differencing, autoregressive, and moving average components make up a non-seasonal ARIMA model, which can be written as a linear equation:

$$Y_t = c + \theta_1 yd_{t-1} + \dots + \theta_p yd_{t-p} + \theta_1 e_{t-1} + \dots + \theta_q e_{t-q} + e_t \quad (3)$$

where yd is Y differenced d times and c is a constant. The particular values of the autoregressive and moving average parameters, in addition to the order of differencing, are often determined by a process known as parameter estimation [25]. This method can also be used to establish the order of differencing. During this stage of the process, the model is fitted to the historical data using the parameter values that produce the lowest amount of residual error. After the model parameters have been estimated, the model can be used to create projections of future values.

B. Seasonal Auto-Regressive Integrated Moving Average

SARIMAX was developed as an ARIMA modification to model and account for seasonality in the data and the effects of external or exogenous variables [26]. Similar to the ARIMA model, SARIMAX incorporates seasonal components in addition to the autoregressive, moving average, and differencing ones. The seasonal components reflect cyclical patterns and trends (daily, weekly, monthly, or yearly cycles) through the use of seasonal autoregressive, moving average, and differencing terms. Exogenous variables, outside of time series, are also included in SARIMAX alongside seasonal effects. The accuracy of forecasts can be improved by including explanatory variables such as weather patterns, economic indicators, and marketing efforts [10]. Moving average and autoregressive models work with stationary and linear data. However, the data are frequently nonstationary. Seasonal ARIMA (SARIMA) is a generalized form of the ARIMA model to handle seasonality in the data. An exogenous regressor term can also be used to incorporate external variables into the model. SARIMAX allows the user to include the effects of external variables in the model. Exogenous variables are variables that influence but are not influenced by a model. The SARIMAX model is represented as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Y(t) = & \mu + \phi(1)Y(t-1) + \dots + \phi(p)Y(t-p) \\
 & -\theta(1)\varepsilon(t-1) - \dots - \theta(q)\varepsilon(t-q) \\
 & +\varphi(1)Y(t-s) + \dots + \varphi(P)Y(t-Ps) \\
 & +\theta(1)\varepsilon(t-s) + \dots + \theta(Q)\varepsilon(t-Qs) \\
 & +\beta X(t) + e(t)
 \end{aligned}
 \quad (4)$$

where, $Y(t)$ is the value of the time series at time t , μ is the mean of the series, $\phi(1)$ through $\phi(p)$ are the autoregressive parameters of the model, $\theta(1)$ through $\theta(q)$ are the moving average parameters of the model, $\varphi(1)$ through $\varphi(P)$ are the seasonal autoregressive parameters, $\theta(1)$ through $\theta(Q)$ are the seasonal moving average parameters, $X(t)$ is the value of the exogenous variable(s) at time t , β is the coefficient(s) for the exogenous variable(s), s is the seasonal period, and $\varepsilon(t)$ is the error term at time t .

The first half of the equation is the same as the ARIMA and represents the auto-regressive and moving average components of the model $(-\theta(q)\varepsilon(t-q))$. This section of the equation begins with the term $-(\theta(q)\varepsilon(t-q))$ and continues until it ends. The seasonal patterns and trends in the data are captured by the following two portions of the equation, which include the seasonal autoregressive and moving average elements, and the seasonal error factors [10, 26]. The effect of extraneous factors on the time series is taken into account in the very last component of the equation, which consists of the exogenous variable(s) and the related coefficient(s). Before the model can be used to create forecasts, the particular values of the parameters ϕ , θ , φ , θ , β and the order of differencing d and e seasonal differencing D must be estimated from the historical data through a process known as parameter estimation. This must be done before the model can be put into use.

C. Linear Regression

Regression is a statistical analysis method to determine the relationship between variables. A dependent variable and one or more independent variables can be modeled using LR. The

purpose of LR is to locate the line or hyperplane that provides the most accurate description of the linear connection that exists between the variables [27]. In the basic regression, as presented in (5), there is just one independent variable X , and one dependent variable Y . The objective is to determine the equation of a line that provides the best possible fit to the data [28].

$$Y = a + bX \quad (5)$$

where b represents the slope of the line and a represents the intercept. Simple LR and multiple LR are both types of linear analysis. The error term accounts for the discrepancies between the predicted and the actual values. LR is used to model and describe the relationship between variables and predict future values of the dependent variable in many different domains, including economics, finance, biology, psychology, and engineering.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Figure 2 presents the methodological flow of this study.

Fig. 2. The proposed methodology flow.

An experimental analysis was carried out to predict urban sprawl and formulate the findings to apply them in wider applications. Based on the methodological flow, after obtaining the dataset for the region of Riyadh from satellite images, the data were subjected to some form of preprocessing. Then the models were used. In the last step, the MAPE measure was used to evaluate the results of the models. The proposed framework used many different datasets, some of which were geographical. These datasets included satellite photos, population data, and land use data. At first, pre-processing was performed to extract key features from the datasets. These key characteristics can then be used to train and test machine learning models.

A. Dataset Generation

Geographic images of Riyadh City and the surrounding area from 1992 to 2022 were used with ArcGIS to obtain historical data on its urban development. The dataset was provided through the Google Earth Engine using the Google Collab program. This dataset was used along with data from 2015 to 2022 from the Copernicus Sentinel-2 satellite. The Geemap, Rasterio, and JSON Python libraries were used to process geospatial images, along with CV2 libraries to process images generated by the Google Earth Engine. Additionally, Matplotlib, NumPy, shutil, and time libraries were used. An object was used to represent the channels in the RGB images and clarify the raw dataset. This object had a set of bands that corresponded to the specified satellite (B4, B3, B2). The scale of the images was determined at 40 m. Data from the specified geographical area were available for a period of eight years, starting in 2015 through 2022. The years 2015 through 2022 were counted as seven years, and the dates January 1, 2022, through June 30, 2022, were added to generate a picture of the eighth year. The mask cloud filter was selected by working with the band QA60, to filter cloud satellite images from the clouds and fog and to ensure that the photographs contain less than 20% cloud cover and fog. When working with photos that have less than 20% blur, the QA60 band was used for filtering, and then these images were divided by 10,000 for normalization. The satellite images were saved in TIFF format. A copy of the satellite images was then created in RGB format to use them in the natural colors that can be seen by the human eye. The generated RGB photos were cut into 150×150 to produce more than 10,000 pieces per image per year, to strike a balance between simplicity and accuracy.

B. Units

The issue posed by the massive urbanization of Riyadh involves thinking about how the geographical coordinates of previous years can be used to gain an understanding of urban growth and make projections about how it will develop in the years to come. Following that, identifying the geographic data to be acquired is the next step in the data collection process. After that, the target or relevant data based on the objective or task was picked. In addition, the unprocessed data were categorized into a variety of forms and dimensions. At first, areas were categorized as either urban or non-urban based on the qualities of the images. The next step was to determine how many hectares are covered by urban and non-urban areas, respectively. A detection program was used to track urban and non-urban areas and determine annual changes. After data organization, the data were transformed into an appropriate form suitable for analysis. The properties of the images were used to make the initial classifications of the locations, which were then broken down further into urban and non-urban regions. Then, the land of the urban and non-urban areas was calculated in hectares, keeping track of the annual change in area size. The images were transformed into data (integer and float). After transforming, data were taken from three columns, Year, Area_by_Hectares, and Increasing rate, as shown in Figure 3 and Table I. Figure 3 shows the entire Riyadh region, including urban and non-urban areas. Non-urban areas are represented in gray, while urban areas are represented in red. The x-axis provides information regarding the length of the

region's borders measured in kilometers. Figure 4 shows the range of the data after transformation.

TABLE I. DATA AFTER TRANSFORMATION

Year	Area_by_Hectares	Increasing_rate
1992	56636	11140
1993	67777	14396
1994	82173	811
1995	82985	1673
1996	84658	1236

Fig. 3. Raw data before transformation.

Fig. 4. Range of data after transformation.

Any missing values were calculated based on the arithmetic mean of the sum of the preceding and the following year.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Before loading the preprocessed data, they were split into a 70:30 ratio for training and testing, respectively. The models were trained with the help of the first portion and then evaluated with the help of the second.

A. Experimental Analysis

The experiment was performed using the Python programming language. The MAPE measure was used to evaluate the models [29], as it expresses the precision by:

$$\text{MAPE} = \frac{100\%}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \left| \frac{A_t - F_t}{A_t} \right| \quad (6)$$

The ARIMA model was run using the following parameters: $p = 1$, $d = 0$, and $q = 2$. The SARIMAX method was run using $p = 4$, $d = 2$, and $q = 3$, however, since the seasonal order was used, the values (0,0,0,0) were employed.

B. Results

A MAPE score of 0% represents a perfect prediction, which means that the projected values exactly match the values that really occurred. When the MAPE is 100%, the projected values are, on average, twice as far apart from the actual values as the actual values themselves are. A more accurate prediction model would have a lower MAPE. The errors from the three models are presented in Table II. The result shows that SARIMAX has the lowest MAPE of 2.0%. MAPE implies that the average absolute percentage difference between the projected and actual values of a dataset is very negligible and the accuracy of a prediction model, represented as a percentage, is within the allowed range. It is essential to take into account the fact that the interpretation in this setting falls within a lower value range of below 3% for one model, however, while using LR, it rose up to 12%, which is still considered to be low.

TABLE II. MAPE COMPARISON BETWEEN ARIMA, SARIMAX, AND LR

ARIMA	SARIMAX	LR
2.2%	2.0%	12.4%

Fig. 5. MAPE of the selected algorithms

SARIMAX was used to predict the urban expansion of the region surrounding Riyadh during the next ten years. This prediction indicates that the region surrounding Riyadh will see tremendous growth, as shown in Table III and Figure 6. In Figure 6, the blue line represents the actual area that has been occupied by the Riyadh region over the past thirty years (1992-2022), while the orange one represents the area that is expected to be occupied in the next 10 years (2023-2032).

TABLE III. THE FORECASTED AREA FOR TEN YEARS

Year	Area_by_Hectar
2023	246622
2024	267250
2025	284135
2026	290721
2027	305200
2028	312984
2029	314570
2030	317563
2031	319888
2032	322039

Fig. 6. The forecasted area for ten years.

V. DISCUSSION

This study used Google Earth Engine [30], and its results indicate that the capital city of KSA, located in the central part of the country, will continue to grow over the next several decades. Although the region surrounding Riyadh is the most extensive in KSA, comprising an area of more than 404,000 km², it is not the most populous city in the country. According to an estimate, the population of the area is projected to be approximately 8.3 million people. Throughout the last few years, the region has seen remarkable development in a variety of fields, including infrastructure, real estate, and tourism. The government has been making large investments in several different infrastructure projects, such as the Riyadh Metro, which will serve as the basis of the city's public transportation system, and the King Salman Energy Park, which will serve as a key hub for the energy industry. Both projects are expected to yield major fruits in the relatively near future. These are some of the most vital details regarding the expansion.

In addition, there is another component of the development that lies ahead. There has been an increase in the number of real estate construction projects in the previous several years. As part of these developments, new residential and commercial properties have been constructed throughout the region. As a direct result of this factor, the real estate market is currently through a period of expansion and prices have been consistently increasing. Tourism is another primary focus for the region and one of the primary objectives of the government is to establish Riyadh as a premier destination for visitors from both within and outside the country. This is yet another component that will contribute to the expansion, and it is also one of the most essential elements for the area. In addition to its many historical and cultural attractions, such as the Masmak Fortress and the National Museum of Saudi Arabia, this region is also known for its vibrant shopping and dining scenes.

According to the findings of this study, it is projected that the Riyadh region will continue to experience growth and development in a range of industries over the next few years. This growth and development is expected to continue for at least the next few years, and the city is expected to become a smart city where even traffic flow will be computerized [31]. This is because the Saudi government is putting a strong emphasis on diversifying the economy and reducing the country's dependence on the revenue from oil sales. The rapid growth of urban areas is a major challenge for many cities around the world [32]. Due to the increase in economic activity and population, there have been major modifications in land use patterns and urban landscapes in recent decades [33]. Therefore, urban planners must find ways to manage and accommodate expanding cities and, along with policymakers, anticipate probable changes in population and land use patterns. Urban growth forecasting is a crucial part of urban

planning. In recent years, machine learning techniques have gained popularity in urban growth models due to their ability to produce extremely accurate estimates [34]. Riyadh is rapidly becoming one of the most populous urban areas, as its population has exploded during the recent decades, causing major changes in building and transportation habits in the area. Therefore, it is important to create predictions about Riyadh's urban growth to guide the city's development and ensure that it meets the needs of its residents.

VI. CONCLUSION

Utilizing the Integrated Regressive Moving Average (ARIMA), the Automatic Seasonal Integrated Regressive Moving Average (SARIMAX), and the Linear Regression (LR), this study performed urban growth forecasts in the region surrounding Riyadh for the next ten years. To do this, we analyzed satellite photos of the Riyadh region taken between 1992 and 2022. We utilized the Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), to analyze the models that were used so that we could choose the model that was most accurate for making realistic predictions. According to the findings, the SARIMAX algorithm was the most effective out of the three algorithms, with a MAPE value of 2.0%. On the other hand, the ARIMA algorithm was the least effective, with a MAPE value of 22%. We can observe that the precision of the developed model really high and produces very good outcomes in comparison to other efforts that are in a similar vein. At the conclusion of the experiment, we used the SARIMAX algorithm to make a prediction regarding the rate of urbanization in the region surrounding Riyadh. According to the projection, the total land area inside the Riyadh region will amount to 322,039 hectares by the year 2032. We propose that as a future endeavour, the data set could be expanded to encompass all regions of Saudi Arabia. Additionally, forecasting can be utilized to generate forecasts for the future in other areas such as population and power consumption.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. Bursztyn, A. L. González, and D. Yanagizawa-Drott, "Misperceived Social Norms: Women Working Outside the Home in Saudi Arabia," *American Economic Review*, vol. 110, no. 10, pp. 2997–3029, Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.20180975>.
- [2] O. H. Sayed and Y. S. Masrahi, "Climatology and phytogeography of Saudi Arabia. A review," *Arid Land Research and Management*, vol. 37, no. 3, pp. 311–368, Jul. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1080/15324982.2023.2169846>.
- [3] M. D. Alotaibi *et al.*, "Assessing the response of five tree species to air pollution in Riyadh City, Saudi Arabia, for potential green belt application," *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, vol. 27, no. 23, pp. 29156–29170, Aug. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-020-09226-w>.
- [4] United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division, *World Urbanization Prospects - The 2018 Revision*. New York, NY, USA: United Nations, 2019.
- [5] M. Arshad, K. M. Khedher, E. M. Eid, and Y. A. Aina, "Evaluation of the urban heat island over Abha-Khamis Mushait tourist resort due to rapid urbanisation in Asir, Saudi Arabia," *Urban Climate*, vol. 36, Mar. 2021, Art. no. 100772, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.uclim.2021.100772>.
- [6] S. Awasthi, "'Hyper'-Urbanisation and migration: A security threat," *Cities*, vol. 108, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 102965, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2020.102965>.
- [7] S. Dinda, K. Das, N. D. Chatterjee, and S. Ghosh, "Integration of GIS and statistical approach in mapping of urban sprawl and predicting future growth in Midnapore town, India," *Modeling Earth Systems and Environment*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 331–352, Mar. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40808-018-0536-8>.
- [8] S. Ghosh, "A city growth and land-use/land-cover change: a case study of Bhopal, India," *Modeling Earth Systems and Environment*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 1569–1578, Dec. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40808-019-00605-y>.
- [9] K. T. Deribew, "Spatiotemporal analysis of urban growth on forest and agricultural land using geospatial techniques and Shannon entropy method in the satellite town of Ethiopia, the western fringe of Addis Ababa city," *Ecological Processes*, vol. 9, no. 1, Sep. 2020, Art. no. 46, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13717-020-00248-3>.
- [10] K. Malarvizhi, S. V. Kumar, and P. Porchelvan, "Urban sprawl modelling and prediction using regression and Seasonal ARIMA: a case study for Vellore, India," *Modeling Earth Systems and Environment*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 1597–1615, Jun. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40808-021-01170-z>.
- [11] L. Xu, X. Liu, D. Tong, Z. Liu, L. Yin, and W. Zheng, "Forecasting Urban Land Use Change Based on Cellular Automata and the PLUS Model," *Land*, vol. 11, no. 5, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.3390/land11050652>.
- [12] W. Boulila, H. Ghandorh, M. A. Khan, F. Ahmed, and J. Ahmad, "A novel CNN-LSTM-based approach to predict urban expansion," *Ecological Informatics*, vol. 64, Sep. 2021, Art. no. 101325, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoinf.2021.101325>.
- [13] X. Liu, X. Wang, K. Chen, and D. Li, "Simulation and prediction of multi-scenario evolution of ecological space based on FLUS model: A case study of the Yangtze River Economic Belt, China," *Journal of Geographical Sciences*, vol. 33, no. 2, pp. 373–391, Feb. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11442-023-2087-9>.
- [14] B. Mahdavi Estalkhsari, P. Mohammad, and A. Karimi, "Land Use and Land Cover Change Dynamics and Modeling Future Urban Growth Using Cellular Automata Model Over Isfahan Metropolitan Area of Iran," in *Ecological Footprints of Climate Change: Adaptive Approaches and Sustainability*, U. Chatterjee, A. O. Akanwa, S. Kumar, S. K. Singh, and A. Dutta Roy, Eds. Cham, Switzerland: Springer International Publishing, 2022, pp. 495–516.
- [15] M. Shrestha, C. Mitra, M. Rahman, and L. Marzen, "Mapping and Predicting Land Cover Changes of Small and Medium Size Cities in Alabama Using Machine Learning Techniques," *Remote Sensing*, vol. 15, no. 1, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs15010106>.
- [16] A. E. AIDousari, A.-A. Kafy, M. Saha, Md. A. Fattah, A. Bakshi, and Z. A. Rahaman, "Summertime Microscale Assessment and Prediction of Urban Thermal Comfort Zone Using Remote-Sensing Techniques for Kuwait," *Earth Systems and Environment*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 435–456, Jun. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41748-023-00340-6>.
- [17] D. Strumsky, L. Bettencourt, and J. Lobo, "Agglomeration effects as spatially embedded social interactions: identifying urban scaling beyond metropolitan areas," *Environment and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City Science*, Jan. 2023, Art. no. 23998083221148200, <https://doi.org/10.1177/23998083221148198>.
- [18] H. B. Akdeniz, N. S. Sag, and S. Inam, "Analysis of land use/land cover changes and prediction of future changes with land change modeler: Case of Belek, Turkey," *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, vol. 195, no. 1, Nov. 2022, Art. no. 135, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-022-10746-w>.
- [19] Y. Gao, Z. Shen, Y. Liu, C. Yu, L. Cui, and C. Song, "Optimization of differentiated regional land development patterns based on urban expansion simulation—A case in China," *Growth and Change*, vol. 54, no. 1, pp. 45–73, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1111/grow.12637>.
- [20] T. He, Y. Lu, W. Yue, W. Xiao, X. Shen, and Z. Shan, "A new approach to peri-urban area land use efficiency identification using multi-source datasets: A case study in 36 Chinese metropolitan areas," *Applied Geography*, vol. 150, Jan. 2023, Art. no. 102826, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apgeog.2022.102826>.
- [21] D. Q. Rutan, P. Hepburn, and M. Desmond, "The Suburbanization of Eviction: Increasing Displacement and Inequality Within American Suburbs," *RSF: The Russell Sage Foundation Journal of the Social*

- Sciences, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 104–125, Feb. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.7758/RSF.2023.9.1.05>.
- [22] A. A. Salam, "Ageing in Saudi Arabia: new dimensions and intervention strategies," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 13, no. 1, Mar. 2023, Art. no. 4035, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-25639-8>.
- [23] R. H. Shumway and D. S. Stoffer, *Time Series Analysis and Its Applications: With R Examples*. Cham, Switzerland: Springer International Publishing, 2017.
- [24] F. Marandi and S. M. T. Fatemi Ghomi, "Time series forecasting and analysis of municipal solid waste generation in Tehran city," in *2016 12th International Conference on Industrial Engineering (ICIE)*, Tehran, Iran, Jan. 2016, pp. 14–18, <https://doi.org/10.1109/INDUSENG.2016.7519343>.
- [25] H. Alabdulrazzaq, M. N. Alenezi, Y. Rawajfih, B. A. Alghannam, A. A. Al-Hassan, and F. S. Al-Anzi, "On the accuracy of ARIMA based prediction of COVID-19 spread," *Results in Physics*, vol. 27, Aug. 2021, Art. no. 104509, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rinp.2021.104509>.
- [26] P. Manigandan *et al.*, "Forecasting Natural Gas Production and Consumption in United States-Evidence from SARIMA and SARIMAX Models," *Energies*, vol. 14, no. 19, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14196021>.
- [27] D. Maulud and A. M. Abdulazeez, "A Review on Linear Regression Comprehensive in Machine Learning," *Journal of Applied Science and Technology Trends*, vol. 1, no. 4, pp. 140–147, Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.38094/jastt1457>.
- [28] A. R. Ramadhan, M. Choi, Y. Chung, and J. Choi, "An Empirical Study of Segmented Linear Regression Search in LevelDB," *Electronics*, vol. 12, no. 4, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics12041018>.
- [29] E. Vivas, H. Allende-Cid, and R. Salas, "A Systematic Review of Statistical and Machine Learning Methods for Electrical Power Forecasting with Reported MAPE Score," *Entropy*, vol. 22, no. 12, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.3390/e22121412>.
- [30] M. Ahmadi and M. Ghamary Asl, "Monitoring urban growth in Google Earth Engine from 1991 to 2021 and predicting in 2041 using CA-MARKOV and geometry: case study—Tehran," *Arabian Journal of Geosciences*, vol. 16, no. 2, Jan. 2023, Art. no. 107, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12517-022-11089-z>.
- [31] S. M. Abdullah *et al.*, "Optimizing Traffic Flow in Smart Cities: Soft GRU-Based Recurrent Neural Networks for Enhanced Congestion Prediction Using Deep Learning," *Sustainability*, vol. 15, no. 7, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15075949>.
- [32] U. Ifiikhar, K. Asrar, M. Waqas, and S. A. Ali, "Evaluating the Performance Parameters of Cryptographic Algorithms for IOT-based Devices," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 7867–7874, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4263>.
- [33] N. B. Serradj, A. D. K. Ali, and M. E. A. Ghernaout, "A Contribution to the Thermal Field Evaluation at the Tool-Part Interface for the Optimization of Machining Conditions," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 7750–7756, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4235>.
- [34] M. U. Farooq, A. Ahmed, S. M. Khan, and M. B. Nawaz, "Estimation of Traffic Occupancy using Image Segmentation," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7291–7295, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4218>.

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Assessing Window Design's Impact on Daylight Uniformity in Classrooms in Patna, India

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ABSTRACT

Windows play a vital role in daylight infusion, significantly impacting indoor visual comfort. Various metrics exist for evaluating visual comfort in which the uniformity ratio falls under the distribution category and is as crucial as illuminance levels. This ratio effectively reduces the likelihood of glare and the need for artificial lighting. The primary objective of this research is to assess the impact of window design on daylight uniformity ratio in a classroom setting. In pursuit of this objective, a study investigated the uniformity ratio (U_o) of north-oriented and south-oriented classrooms of Kendriya Vidyalaya (KV) Khagual, Patna. The study considered five common shapes of windows (excluding the existing base cases) at different window-sill levels. Ninety simulations were run in the DesignBuilder software under overcast, intermediate, and clear sky conditions. To assess the uniformity ratio on three dates: March 21st, June 21st, and December 21st, which correspond to the highest, equinox, and lowest solar availability during the year under intermediate and clear sky conditions at three distinct times. The omission of the specific time and date for overcast conditions and the particular year for clear and intermediate sky conditions is justified as the outcome remains consistent throughout all years. The results show that the window design and sill level significantly affect the uniformity ratio. The research findings show that window design in Case 9 at a sill of 1230 mm and lintel of 3050 mm (just below the slab) consistently produces the best uniformity ratio across all sky conditions, independent of classroom orientation. This paper offers valuable design recommendations by comparing the uniformity ratio for five commonly used window designs. This is one of the first studies of window design and position to evaluate the uniformity ratio in the classrooms at Patna.

Keywords-window design; uniformity ratio; daylight; classroom; simulation

I. INTRODUCTION

Window design is a crucial aspect of daylighting in buildings. Well-designed windows can significantly impact the distribution of natural light, enhancing visual comfort and reducing the need for artificial lighting during daylight hours. Positioning, size, and shape of windows influence the amount of daylight that enters the space and the way it is distributed. Strategic window design allows optimal daylight penetration while minimizing glare and unwanted heat gain. In comparison to artificial electric light, natural daylight provides occupants with enhanced visual comfort [1]. As a result, daylight plays a pivotal role in window design, offering the potential for passive solutions that improve energy efficiency and visual comfort

[2]. The effective utilization of daylighting in buildings can be ensured by conducting daylight performance analysis and integrating the results into the building facade design process [3]. Additionally, it represents a notable architectural strategy in creating visually comfortable classrooms, enhancing circadian activity and reading-writing speed, and positively influencing the well-being of students and teachers [4]. A well-lit building with natural light and solar radiation for heating and cooling reduces electricity demand, offers comfortable indoor temperatures, and lowers energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions [5-7]. Efficiently utilizing solar radiation allows buildings to create a comfortable and productive indoor environment while promoting energy saving and sustainability [8].

In classrooms, daylight evaluation encompasses several metrics, including static evaluation (illuminance and daylight factor) and dynamic evaluation (useful daylight illuminance, daylight autonomy, continuous daylight autonomy, spatial daylight autonomy), based on the analysis period (point-in-time vs. annual), sky model (standard vs climate based) [6], and distribution (illuminance uniformity) [9]. Out of these, the uniformity ratio is especially critical for classrooms, as insufficient uniformity can lead to glare and increased dependence on artificial lighting [10]. Research demonstrates a preference for classrooms with uniform daylighting, even if the illuminance levels are lower, as opposed to an uneven distribution of light with higher illuminance. Achieving a uniformity ratio in a side-lit classroom is challenging. The illuminance levels decline as one walks away from the window, and there is a considerable drop in illuminance at the opposite corner of the classroom, reducing the uniformity ratio.

This paper focuses primarily on the north and south orientations due to the substantial differences in daylight supply between these two directions in the northern hemisphere. The southern orientation receives abundant direct sunlight, while the northern orientation benefits from diffused sunlight. These two orientations present a notable contrast for investigation. The current study is limited to north and south-oriented classrooms. The East-West orientations remain open to future exploration and research. The study at hand is one of the first studies of window design and position (sill level) to evaluate the uniformity ratio in the south and north-oriented classrooms in composite climate at KV Khagual, Patna, which previous researchers ignored. This research introduces a new perspective to investigate the impact of window design and position (window-sill) on the uniformity ratio and adds existing knowledge of daylight uniformity. The findings of this research are specific contributions in this field.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Table I provides a concise overview of the past research on design proposals of varying categories and building types.

TABLE I. WINDOW/FACADE CONFIGURATION LITERATURE

Design proposal	Category	Building type	References
Energy, thermal, visual performance	Window configuration	Office	[11-14]
Energy and visual performance	Window configuration	Classroom	[15-17]
Energy, thermal, visual performance	Window configuration	Residential	[18-20]
Energy and visual performance	Window configuration	Non-residential	[21]
Energy, thermal, visual performance	Facade configuration	School	[22]
Energy and visual performance	Facade configuration	Residential	[23]
Energy and visual performance	Facade configuration	Office	[24]
Energy and visual performance	Window configuration	-	[25-26]

This research aimed to improve the visual performance of buildings using static and dynamic metrics. The literature

review revealed that window/facade configurations significantly impact the buildings' visual performance. The climate and window orientation influence the outcomes, leading to varying results. Horizontal windows exhibited superior illuminance uniformity and increased energy savings for electrical lighting. On the other hand, higher-positioned (sill) windows facilitated deeper penetration of daylight into indoor spaces. Furthermore, centrally placed windows at eye level provided favourable outside views. The daylight factor also gives more residential satisfaction [27, 28].

III. METHODOLOGY

This study examines daylight uniformity resulting from window design and position (sill level). It specifically focuses on investigating the effects of commonly utilized window shapes and positions in classrooms situated within the composite climate of India. The research process involves several steps. Firstly, it entails creating a model of the classroom geometry, including all window configurations ranging from case 1 to case 10, within the DesignBuilder software. In the second step, simulations are conducted under three distinct conditions: clear, intermediate, and overcast sky. The simulations were performed for March 21st, June 21st, and December 21st, corresponding to the highest, equinox and lowest solar availability during the year for the intermediate and clear sky conditions at three distinct times: 9:00 a.m., 12:00 p.m., and 3:00 p.m. The impact of different window designs and position (sill level) on uniformity ratios are analyzed. A total of 10 cases were investigated, with 5 cases featuring centrally located windows while maintaining the existing sill and lintel levels and the other 5 cases having windows at elevated positions (sill level). Figure 1 depicts the opted research workflow.

Fig. 1. Research workflow.

A. Window Design and Position

This study involves selecting various window designs and window sills for the classrooms under investigation. Five commonly used window designs were considered. Figure 2 illustrates the window design (plan and elevation) with sill and lintel level. Figure 3 illustrates the 10 cases of window design of the same window-to-wall ratio (WWR) of 40.23% with alternative 01 from Case 1 to 5 and alternative 02 from Case 6 to 10. In alternative 01, the sill and window height are kept fixed to match the existing conditions, creating what is referred to as a centrally located window. In alternative 02, the windows are elevated, with the top positioned just below the classroom ceiling. For Cases 1 to 5, the window sill is 800 mm, and the lintel is kept at 2620 mm, whereas from Cases 6 to 10, the

window sill is 1230 mm, and the lintel is 3050 mm (just below the slab).

The KV Khagul classrooms adhere to the standards and guidelines regarding area and dimension, which are common throughout the country. The selected KV school is located in Khagul, Patna, Bihar, India, with coordinates of 25°35'05.00"N and 85°01'56.80"E. The classroom has dimensions of 7 m × 7 m, covering an area of 49 m², with floor-to-floor height equal to 3.30 m. It is situated on the ground floor, has side lighting, and is oriented towards the south. Figure 2 displays the typical plan and the elevation of the window side wall of a classroom.

The single-pane clear glass windows in this classroom has dimensions of 2360 mm × 1820 mm and a WWR of 40.23%.

Fig. 2. (a) Class design, (b) elevation (window side wall).

Fig. 3. Window design and position (sill level).

TABLE II. MATERIAL REFLECTANCE AND TRANSMITTANCE

Particular	Reflectivity
Walls	0.75
Ceiling	0.80
Floor	0.20
Glass (transmittance)	0.80 (transmittance)

The CIE [29] model is more accurate than the Perez model [30] in predicting sky luminance in Indian tropical conditions, provided the correct CIE sky type is known. This model's capability to match the actual sky conditions in the region enhances the reliability of daylight simulations and analysis [31]. For this study, the CIE clear day, CIE intermediate day, and CIE overcast day sky conditions were chosen for simulation. These sky conditions were selected to replicate the typical sky conditions experienced in India throughout the year.

B. Uniformity Metric

Illuminance Uniformity or Uniformity Ratio (U_o) is a metric expressed as the ratio between the minimum illuminance value on a given plane (E_{min}) and the average illuminance (E_{avg}) at that specific moment. Alternatively, in certain cases, the ratio can be defined as the ratio between the minimum (E_{min}) and maximum (E_{max}) illuminance values on the same plane, so it is essential to specify the definition used [32].

$$U_{o,avg} = \frac{E_{min}}{E_{avg}} \tag{1}$$

$$U_{o,max} = \frac{E_{min}}{E_{max}} \tag{2}$$

According to the guidelines set by the Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method (BREEAM), the uniformity ratio can be expressed as the Minimum Daylight Factor (DF_{min}) divided by the Average Daylight Factor (DF_{avg}). Table III outlines the prescribed threshold values for the uniformity ratio in the classroom.

TABLE III. RECOMMENDED ILLUMINANCE UNIFORMITY STANDARDS FOR CLASSROOMS

Particular	Uniformity ($U_{o,avg}$)	Reference
Classrooms, tutorial rooms	> 0.6	[33]
General teaching	0.8	[34]
Task area	> 0.6	[35]
Side lit classroom	0.3-0.4	[34]

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figures 4-7 illustrate the uniformity ratio for south and north-oriented classrooms under clear and intermediate sky conditions on 21st of March, 21st of June, and 21st of December, at 9:00 a.m., 12:00 p.m., and 3:00 p.m. The omission of the specific year is justified as the outcome remains consistent throughout all years. Figures 8 and 9 illustrate the uniformity

ratio for south and north-oriented classrooms under overcast sky. By analyzing the data depicted in Figures 4-9, one can gain valuable insights into the daylight performance of the south and north-oriented classrooms and the impact of window design and position (sill level) on achieving uniform illumination throughout the space under all three sky conditions. Window design and position in Case No. 9, as shown in Figure 3 achieve the highest uniformity ratio in all conditions. Additionally, specific window shapes and positions yield elevated uniformity ratios when placed at higher sill levels, resulting in values slightly exceeding 0.6 for the north-oriented classroom under clear sky condition. The window design and position shown in Case No. 1 give the lowest uniformity ratio among all cases.

Fig. 4. Uniformity ratio for a south-oriented classroom under clear sky.

Fig. 5. Uniformity ratio for a south-oriented classroom under intermediate sky.

Fig. 6. Uniformity ratio for a north-oriented classroom under clear sky.

Fig. 7. Uniformity ratio for a north-oriented classroom under intermediate sky.

Fig. 8. Uniformity ratio for a south-oriented classroom under overcast sky.

Fig. 9. Uniformity ratio for a north-oriented classroom under overcast sky.

A. Impact of Window Design and Position on the Uniformity Ratio

In Case 9, where the windows are placed at a higher sill level of 1230 mm, the north-oriented classroom under clear sky achieves a 0.6 or more uniformity ratio in March and December and more than 0.5 in June. Window design in Case 10 exhibits almost the same uniformity ratio as in Case 9. The same window design with a higher sill level achieves a more uniformity ratio than a lower sill level. The window designs in Cases 6-10 with higher sill level (1230 mm) achieve approximately 0.3 or more uniformity ratio in all three-sky conditions in both orientations. From Case 1 to Case 5, centrally located windows yield uniformity ratios ranging from 0.21 to 0.48 at various times and months. Case 7 ranks third in providing higher uniformity ratios for both orientations.

B. Impact of Sky Condition on the Uniformity Ratio

The uniformity ratio (U_o) obtains a value of 0.67 under clear sky, which is characterized by dominating radiation, which is the greatest among the other sky situations in the north-oriented classroom. The highest uniformity ratio under intermediate sky was 0.438 and 0.411 and was observed for Case 9 on the 21st of December in the north-and south-oriented classroom, respectively. Conversely, the lowest U_o value of 0.234 was recorded for Case 1 on the 21st of March at 9:00 a.m. in the south-oriented classroom. Under overcast sky, where direct radiation is absent, the highest U_o of 0.37 is observed for the north-oriented classroom in Case 9. Conversely, the lowest U_o value of 0.248 is recorded for Case 1 in the south-oriented classroom under the same sky conditions.

C. Impact of Orientation on the Uniformity Ratio

The impact of the classroom orientation on the uniformity ratio is apparent; north-oriented classrooms achieve approximately more U_o value than south-oriented classrooms under all three sky conditions. The impact of orientation on the U_o is more evident, particularly when comparing north-oriented classrooms with south-oriented classrooms under clear sky conditions. In north-oriented classrooms, there is more variation in the uniformity ratio. Under intermediate sky

conditions, the variation in uniformity ratio between north and south-oriented classrooms is less pronounced compared to the clear sky conditions. This suggests that the distribution of daylight is more consistent in both orientations when a mix of direct and diffused sunlight characterizes the sky condition. Under overcast sky, the impact of orientation on the uniformity ratio is minimal, as both north and south-oriented classrooms tend to exhibit similar trends, because the sky is heavily clouded, with no direct sunlight in overcast sky conditions. Instead, the sky acts as a significant diffused light source, providing relatively uniform lighting across the space.

V. CONCLUSION

The present study has assessed the impact of window design on daylight uniformity and uniformity ratio in a classroom setting. A comparative experiment was conducted using simulations to analyze the impact of window design and sill on three typical days and times for north-oriented and south-oriented classrooms of KV Khagual, Patna. Various configurations of rectangular window forms were examined, with two sill heights (800 mm and 1230 mm) while maintaining a consistent window-to-wall ratio (WWR). The research findings show that window design in Case 9 at a sill of 1230 mm and lintel of 3050 mm (just below the slab) consistently produces the best uniformity ratio for all sky conditions, independent of classroom orientation. This research emphasizes the importance of window sill in improving daylight distribution and visual comfort in a classroom. Placing windows strategically at high sill heights allows for equal dispersion of natural light, resulting in a comfortable and well-lit learning environment for students and teachers. This method improves homogeneity and optimizes lighting performance in educational areas.

It is important to note that the results of this study are based on a limited set of sky conditions, window shapes, and placements. Therefore, future research should investigate a broader range of window designs of east and west orientations under varying sky circumstances to assess their influence on the uniformity ratio while considering elements like WWR, window sill, and other architectural solutions. Researchers may get deeper insights into the link between window design, daylight uniformity, daylight performance, and visual comfort by performing more extensive studies, allowing them to develop more successful daylighting techniques for various building types contexts.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. D. Galasiu and J. A. Veitch, "Occupant preferences and satisfaction with the luminous environment and control systems in daylight offices: a literature review," *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 38, no. 7, pp. 728–742, Jul. 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2006.03.001>.
- [2] Y.-W. Lim, M. Z. Kandar, M. H. Ahmad, D. R. Ossen, and A. M. Abdullah, "Building facade design for daylighting quality in typical government office building," *Building and Environment*, vol. 57, pp. 194–204, Nov. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2012.04.015>.
- [3] F. S. Yilmaz, "Proposal of a facade design approach for daylight performance determination in buildings," *AJ Z ITU Journal of the Faculty of Architecture*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 57–64, Aug. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.5505/itujfa.2016.49140>.
- [4] Heschong Mahone Group, "Daylighting in Schools: An Investigation into the Relationship Between Daylighting and Human Performance Detailed Report," Pacific Gas and Electric Company, 1999.
- [5] X. Yu and Y. Su, "Daylight availability assessment and its potential energy saving estimation –A literature review," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 52, pp. 494–503, Dec. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.07.142>.
- [6] N. S. Shafavi, M. Tahsildoost, and Z. S. Zomorodian, "Investigation of illuminance-based metrics in predicting occupants' visual comfort (case study: Architecture design studios)," *Solar Energy*, vol. 197, pp. 111–125, Feb. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2019.12.051>.
- [7] I. Zeghib and A. Chaker, "Efficiency of a Solar Hydronic Space Heating System under the Algerian Climate," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 6, no. 6, pp. 1274–1279, Dec. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.875>.
- [8] J. Yau, J. J. Wei, H. Wang, O. Eniola, and F. P. Ibitoye, "Modeling of the Internal Temperature for an Energy Saving Chinese Solar Greenhouse," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 6276–6281, Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3728>.
- [9] S. Carlucci, F. Causone, F. De Rosa, and L. Pagliano, "A review of indices for assessing visual comfort with a view to their use in optimization processes to support building integrated design," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 47, pp. 1016–1033, Jul. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.03.062>.
- [10] S. Zanon, N. Callegaro, and R. Albatici, "A Novel Approach for the Definition of an Integrated Visual Quality Index for Residential Buildings," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 9, no. 8, Jan. 2019, Art. no. 1579, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app9081579>.
- [11] Y. Zhai, Y. Wang, Y. Huang, and X. Meng, "A multi-objective optimization methodology for window design considering energy consumption, thermal environment and visual performance," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 134, pp. 1190–1199, Apr. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2018.09.024>.
- [12] M. Qingsong and H. Fukuda, "Parametric Office Building for Daylight and Energy Analysis in the Early Design Stages," *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 216, pp. 818–828, Jan. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.12.079>.
- [13] A. Maleki and N. Dehghan, "Optimum Characteristics of Windows in an Office Building in Isfahan for Save Energy and Preserve Visual Comfort," *Journal of Daylighting*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 222–238, Jul. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.15627/jd.2021.18>.
- [14] S. Farivar and S. Teimourtash, "Impact of Window Design on Dynamic Daylight Performance in an Office Building in Iran," *Journal of Daylighting*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 31–44, Mar. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.15627/jd.2023.3>.
- [15] Z. S. Zomorodian, S. S. Korsavi, and M. Tahsildoost, "The effect of window configuration on daylight performance in classrooms: A field and simulation study," *International journal of architectural engineering and urban planning*, vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 15–24, 2016.
- [16] B. J. Futrell, E. C. Ozelkan, and D. Brentrup, "Bi-objective optimization of building enclosure design for thermal and lighting performance," *Building and Environment*, vol. 92, pp. 591–602, Oct. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2015.03.039>.
- [17] X. Liu, Y. Sun, S. Wei, L. Meng, and G. Cao, "Illumination distribution and daylight glare evaluation within different windows for comfortable lighting," *Results in Optics*, vol. 3, May 2021, Art. no. 100080, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rjo.2021.100080>.
- [18] S. Carlucci, G. Cattarin, F. Causone, and L. Pagliano, "Multi-objective optimization of a nearly zero-energy building based on thermal and visual discomfort minimization using a non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm (NSGA-II)," *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 104, pp. 378–394, Oct. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2015.06.064>.
- [19] I. Acosta, M. A. Campano, and J. F. Molina, "Window design in architecture: Analysis of energy savings for lighting and visual comfort in residential spaces," *Applied Energy*, vol. 168, pp. 493–506, Apr. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2016.02.005>.

- [20] F. Kharvari, "A Field-validated Multi-objective Optimization of the Shape and Size of Windows Based on Daylighting Metrics in Hot-summer Mediterranean and Dry Summer Continental Climates," *Journal of Daylighting*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 222–237, Nov. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.15627/jd.2020.19>.
- [21] B. Lartigue, B. Lasternas, and V. Loftness, "Multi-objective optimization of building envelope for energy consumption and daylight," *Indoor and Built Environment*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 70–80, Feb. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1177/1420326X13480224>.
- [22] A. Zhang, R. Bokel, A. van den Dobbelsteen, Y. Sun, Q. Huang, and Q. Zhang, "Optimization of thermal and daylight performance of school buildings based on a multi-objective genetic algorithm in the cold climate of China," *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 139, pp. 371–384, Mar. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2017.01.048>.
- [23] A. Toutou, M. Fikry, and W. Mohamed, "The parametric based optimization framework daylighting and energy performance in residential buildings in hot arid zone," *Alexandria Engineering Journal*, vol. 57, no. 4, pp. 3595–3608, Dec. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aej.2018.04.006>.
- [24] C. E. Ochoa, M. B. C. Aries, E. J. van Loenen, and J. L. M. Hensen, "Considerations on design optimization criteria for windows providing low energy consumption and high visual comfort," *Applied Energy*, vol. 95, pp. 238–245, Jul. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2012.02.042>.
- [25] I. Acosta, C. Munoz, M. A. Campano, and J. Navarro, "Analysis of daylight factors and energy saving allowed by windows under overcast sky conditions," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 77, pp. 194–207, May 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2014.12.017>.
- [26] S. Saadi and A. Chaker, "A Numerical Simulation Approach for Sunspot Area Calculation," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 3013–3017, Jun. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2038>.
- [27] S. Kumari, A. Kumar, R. Kumar, and A. H. M. Fetais, "Assessing residential satisfaction parameters and its socio-economic characteristics of low-income group public housing in Lucknow city," *International Journal of Indian Culture and Business Management*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 335–352, Jan. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJICBM.2023.132448>.
- [28] S. Kumari, A. Kumar, and R. Kumar, "Regression model for residential satisfaction in low-income group public housing in Lucknow, India," *International Journal of Indian Culture and Business Management*, vol. 1, Jun. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJICBM.2022.10050006>.
- [29] S. Darula and R. Kittler, "CIE general sky standard defining luminance distributions," in *Proceedings of eSim 2002 The Canadian conference on building energy*, Montreal, Canada, Sep. 2002.
- [30] R. Perez, R. Seals, and J. Michalsky, "All-weather model for sky luminance distribution—Preliminary configuration and validation," *Solar Energy*, vol. 50, no. 3, pp. 235–245, Mar. 1993, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-092X\(93\)90017-I](https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-092X(93)90017-I).
- [31] N. A. Khan, P. Malik, and B. Bhattacharjee, "Identifying the design skies for Indian tropical climatic conditions," *Current Science*, vol. 119, no. 3, pp. 473–484, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.18520/cs/v119/i3/473-484>.
- [32] V. Costanzo, G. Evola, and L. Marletta, "A Review of Daylighting Strategies in Schools: State of the Art and Expected Future Trends," *Buildings*, vol. 7, no. 2, Jun. 2017, Art. no. 41, <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings7020041>.
- [33] *BS EN 12464-1 (2021), Light and lighting — Lighting of work places, Part 1: Indoor work places*. London, UK: British Standards Institution, 2021.
- [34] D. Loe, N. Watson, E. Rowlands, K. Mansfield, B. Venning, and J. Baker, "Lighting Design for Schools. Building Bulletin 90," The Stationery Office, London, UK, Building Bulletin 90, 1999.
- [35] K. Butcher, *Lighting Guide 5: Lighting for Education*. London, UK: Chartered Institution of Building Services Engineers, 2011.

A Recommendation Engine Model for Giant Social Media Platforms using a Probabilistic Approach

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ABSTRACT

Existing recommender system algorithms often find it difficult to interpret and, as a result, to extract meaningful recommendations from social media. Because of this, there is a growing demand for more powerful algorithms that are able to extract information from low-dimensional spaces. One such approach would be the cutting-edge matrix factorization technique. Facebook is one of the most widely used social networking platforms. It has more than one billion monthly active users who engage with each other on the platform by sharing status updates, images, events, and other types of content. Facebook's mission includes fostering stronger connections between individuals, and to that end, the platform employs techniques from recommender systems in an effort to better comprehend the actions and patterns of its users, after which it suggests forming new connections with other users. However, relatively little study has been done in this area to investigate the low-dimensional spaces included within the black box system by employing methods such as matrix factorization. Using a probabilistic matrix factorization approach, the interactions that users have with the posts of other users, such as liking, commenting, and other similar activities, were utilized in an effort to generate a list of potential friends that the user who is the focus of this work may not yet be familiar with. The proposed model performed better in terms of suggestion accuracy in comparison to the original matrix factorization, which resulted in the creation of a recommendation list that contained more correct information.

Keywords-artificial intelligence; machine learning; recommender systems; probabilistic models; social media

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's internet, the flow of information is constantly expanding, reaching a point where it makes the information in question notably scarce. As a result, it can be difficult for recommender systems to handle the information in an effective and correct manner. On social media sites, individuals connect in a variety of ways, each of which is unique to the user. Some consumers give the recommender system a great deal of detailed and specific information regarding their preferences and wants, which makes the task at hand relatively simple. On the other side, there are some users who rarely directly submit their preferences and choices to the system, making the task of the recommender system in trying to comprehend those users more difficult. Examples of preferences and choices include demographic information and interests. Recommender systems, in general, consist of many types [1], but the most popular are

content-based recommender systems and collaborative filtering recommender systems [2-4]. Content-based recommender systems construct their recommendation models based purely on information that is contained within the content itself, such as product descriptions, car colors, movie actors, book authors, users' genders, ages, etc., among other things [5-7]. This necessitates the availability of information in order for the recommender system to carry out its duties in an appropriate manner. The other widely used technique for recommender systems is called collaborative filtering. This technique requires the participation of either users or things in order to compile a list of recommendations. Using the behavior of other users who are similar to the target user, this method analyzes user behavior in an effort to better understand it and then makes product recommendations to that user. Based on this idea, this technique requires users to explicitly show their preferences by doing things like rating more movies, purchasing more

products, watching extra clips, etc. This is done so that the recommender system can find similar users or similar items and attempt to build a recommendation list for that user or item based on that similarity, which is all done from the perspective of collaboration. The well-known "cold start" problem can be solved by using the approaches of content-based recommender systems. However, in terms of purely collaborative filtering, this problem has not been resolved [8]. Recommender systems methodologies help in other aspects of life such as agriculture production and other industries [9].

In addition to helping users connect with new people and develop new relationships, one of the purposes of social media platforms is to provide a forum in which users can freely express their thoughts. For this reason, these platforms make use of recommender system techniques to assist in understanding the behavior of their consumers and to recommend new partnerships in an effort to keep users actively engaged on their platforms in order to achieve business goals. As mentioned above, social media platforms have not yet explored the use of probabilistic-wise low-dimensional latent spaces. Due to this, in this paper, we attempt to take advantage of this technique and recommend a more accurate relationship list for the target user, even with a small number of interactions using a probabilistic approach.

In this research, we used a real Facebook dataset to investigate a technique called Probabilistic Matrix Factorization (PMF) [10], with the goal of developing a recommendation engine that is more accurate.

The research questions that we are attempting to address are: Can we crawl the Facebook platform and extract associations between users based on the interactions that they have had with one another using a probabilistic model even when the data are sparse? Is it feasible to determine whether or not two users who have not yet become friends will get along based on how they engage with the friends they share in common? The purpose of this study is to investigate these topics by doing experiments using a real dataset from Facebook.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Probabilistic Machine Learning

In the field of machine learning, PMF has been integrated into a large number of research projects and further improved through those initiatives. Authors in [11] investigated PMF in order to develop a recommendation model that overcomes the cold start problem and reduced the mistake rate by employing the concept of user trust. According to the authors, if two users X and Y are friends, then they trust each other to a certain degree, depending on the total interaction that each user has had on that platform. When compared to the baseline models, the model demonstrated significantly better performance [11]. Authors in [12] studied how PMF may increase the effectiveness of recommendation engines while keeping in mind that the absence of data is not a random occurrence. They asserted that the majority of the existing algorithms for matrix factorization take into account the possibility that missing data are randomly dispersed across the dataset that was evaluated. However, if a user only interacts with things that interest him

or her and ignores everything else, then the missing data are not random. This indicates that the performance of existing models, which assume that missing data are always arranged in a random order, will be skewed. They assert that the proposed strategy is superior to correspondence models in terms of performance. Authors in [13] broaden the usage of PMF to not only recommend a new item to the target user, but also provide a method that analyzes numerous datasets, as well as models, and predicts the performance of such datasets in such models. In addition to this, they used PMF to recommend a new item to the target user. The final model displayed encouraging performance indicators. According to [14, 15], the preferences of users have a vital influence on the improvement of the performance of recommendation engines. The authors demonstrated that the accuracy of a suggestion list may be improved by employing PMF in conjunction with the incorporation of preferred preferences during the process of developing the model. The findings that their model produced were superior to the baselines. According to [16], supplementary information and graphs are another type of supporting content that can assist PMF models in improving their overall performance. According to [17], the addition of side information for both users and items in the PMF models by utilizing the power of convolutional neural networks not only improves the model performance, but also resolves well-known issues within the recommender systems research field such as cold start and sparse data. The authors conducted their analysis of the suggested model utilizing three different datasets, namely MovieLens 100K, MovieLens 1M, and HetRec 2011. The findings revealed that, in comparison to the baselines, the outputs provided by the proposed model were significantly more promising.

B. Probabilistic Matrix Factorization in Social Media

PMF has been implemented in a variety of fields, including medical, social media, image annotation, and other applications [18]. The new model has been proposed in [19] uses PMF to make predictions about the likelihood of a long-non-coding RNA (lncRNA) disease relationship for certain individuals. Constructing three distinct association networks connected to lncRNA, then preprocessing those networks with the KNN method, and finally obtaining a weighted version of the lncRNA are the objectives of this project. After that, PMF generates a likelihood that the lncRNA in question is associated with the target patient. They investigated the model with a variety of datasets pertaining to cancer-related diseases, such as breast, lung, and colorectal cancer, as a means of conducting additional testing on the model. When compared to various baselines, their model produced some encouraging findings. The accuracy of the PMF was also employed by the authors in [20] to calculate the likelihood of an association between certain medications and diseases like diabetes, cardiovascular disease, and neoplasms. They began by constructing a matrix that represented drug-to-disease linkages via the target-pathway-gene midway. This allowed them to make an educated guess as to the likelihood that particular medications are responsible for particular diseases. The new model performed better than the previous model when precision and area under curve metrics were taken into consideration. Using an extended version of PMF designed specifically for the purpose of

addressing the image-to-word correlation problem, authors in [21] suggested a solution to the problem. They built a latent space matrix for determining the links between images and words. When compared to existing state-of-the-art models utilizing the Flickr and Corel datasets, the developed model correctly predicted more accurate words annotated to images.

Authors in [22] drew attention to the problem of data scarcity in today's internet and explained how the performance of recommender systems can be influenced in terms of prediction accuracy. They also claimed that the present social recommendation algorithms rely solely on a two-way trust relationship between users. Nevertheless, in their method, they included information about topical attention and confidence in the PMF model and the neural network. This resulted in the extraction of several features that assisted the recommender system in functioning more effectively. They tested their proposed model by comparing its accuracy to that of two different real-world datasets, and the results demonstrated that their model's performance was superior to that of some of the most recent models. Authors in [23] discussed the sparsity problem that occurs in recommendation engines in the social realm. They underlined that the accuracy of predictions and the scalability of current collaborative recommender systems are two additional difficulties that collaborative recommender systems struggle with. In an effort to find a solution to these problems, they suggested a probabilistic model that, in addition to rating history, makes use of social information regarding the users of the system. The goal of this model was to assist systems in better understanding their users and, as a result, in providing more accurate recommendations. When testing the model, they compared it to methods that were considered to be state-of-the-art and discovered that their model performed significantly better, especially when dealing with sparse data. It is possible to gain an understanding of the behavior of users on a particular platform by analyzing activities that take place on social networks (such as Twitter and Facebook), such as retweets [24]. In order to construct a prediction model with PMF, authors in [24] created a model that not only takes into account social influence and the semantics of the text, but also activities like retweeting. Their proposed method proved to be superior to existing models that are considered to be state-of-the-art.

When it comes to combating the sparsity problem that adversely impacts the efficiency of recommendation engines, one body of research emphasizes the significance of the ancillary information that social platforms make available, such as tags, ratings, and the reciprocal relationships that exist between users. In [26], the regularization terms that were described earlier were incorporated into the PMF algorithm so that it could take into account the side information. During the evaluation, the authors trained and evaluated the suggested model by making use of the Last.fm dataset. They used the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) metrics to determine how accurate the recommendations were. The findings indicate that their proposed model is superior to the baseline models in terms of performance. Authors in [27] created a framework to analyze tweets in an effort to prevent the spread of SARS-CoV-2 Omicron variant, highlighting the significance of social media

in machine learning development. A black box recommendation model was suggested in [28] utilizing the MF approach [29] and applying it to a real Facebook dataset. In the current research we extend that by introducing a probability methodology that makes use of the PMF technique [10], and we do so while utilizing the same data.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this research, we investigate the efficacy of the PMF algorithm in predicting possible interactions between users on Facebook [10]. Users on Facebook connect with one another by giving likes to posts, commenting on photographs, and other similar activities. These interactions can be extended in latent spaces for both users and their friends with hidden features, which ultimately leads to the prediction of how each user will interact with all other users and, as a result, the discovery of reasonable matches. An illustration of the proposed model can be seen in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. An illustration of the proposed model beginning with crawling the real data from Facebook and ending with the production of recommendation lists.

The PMF makes use of the Gaussian distribution or the normal distribution in order to observe expected friendship interactions. The following is a representation of the conditional distribution based on the observed interactions:

$$p(R|U, F, \sigma^2) = \prod_{i=1}^u \prod_{j=1}^f I_{i,j} [N(R_{i,j} | g(U_i F_j^T), \sigma^2)] \quad (1)$$

The value of $R_{i,j}$ conveys the frequency with which user i communicates with friend j . U and F refer to the user and friend latent spaces, while u and f are, respectively, the user set and the friend set. The probability density of the Gaussian distribution is denoted by the expression $N(R_{i,j} | g(U_i F_j^T), \sigma^2)$. The variance is denoted by σ^2 , and the terminating factor is denoted by $I_{i,j}$. The terminating factor has a value of 1 if user i interacts with friend j , and a value of 0 if they do not. $t(x) = \frac{x-1}{N-1}$ is the formula that is used to normalize the interactions such that they sum up to 1, where N is the maximum number of times that two users in our dataset have interacted with one another, which is 84. In addition, the following are the two-zero-mean spherical Gaussian priors that apply to the vectors of both users and friends:

$$p(U|\sigma_U^2) = \prod_{i=1}^u [N(U_i | (U_i | 0, \sigma_U^2 I))] \quad (2)$$

$$p(F|\sigma_F^2) = \prod_{j=1}^f [N(F_j | (F_j | 0, \sigma_F^2 I))] \quad (3)$$

The log of the afterward distribution over users and friends can be obtained by:

$$\frac{p(U, F | R, \sigma R2, \sigma U2, \sigma F2)}{p(R | U, F, \sigma R2) p(U | \sigma U2) p(F | \sigma F2)} \propto \quad (4)$$

The idea behind the PMF technique is that as the training process progresses, the data distribution of users' friendships and interactions becomes more accurate. The future interactions predicted between users in each training cycle are fed into the subsequent training cycle until both the previous and subsequent predictions converge, and similarity becomes high, at which point the training process should be terminated. As a result, PMF will generate a prediction for all users' mutual interactions even though expressed interactions are few and sparse. We tested this notion using a real dataset crawled from the Facebook platform, which has not been investigated previously in this context. In the following section, we will present our experimental findings. The code is available on GitHub [25].

IV. RESULT ANALYSIS

A. Dataset

We required a real dataset from an asynchronous social network to validate the accuracy of our methodology and evaluate its results. Facebook is the largest social network that provides bidirectional friendship connections, which is the focus of our study. We developed a web crawler to retrieve publicly accessible Facebook users' profiles. The crawler retrieves the users' data and their friends' profiles and proceeds to retrieve profiles of friends of friends. We collected the list of genuine friends with bi-directional relationships, but we did not collect follow connections or other one-directional relationships. To acquire an effective dataset, we ran our web crawler on various user IDs (seeds) from various regions of the United States and the United Kingdom. After one month, we stopped our crawler and as a result we have fetched a total of 16500 user profiles. If any portion of a user's data is not publicly accessible, an empty list will be displayed. For instance, if a user sets his/her friends list to private, his/her friends list will appear as an empty list in our dataset. In addition, for privacy and to ensure anonymity, user IDs are substituted with randomly generated numeric IDs. Every user profile we retrieved from our dataset contains the user ID, friends list, gender, place of origin, self-reported interests, and interactions on posts which are comments and/or likes. For each retrieved post, we collected the post ID and the user IDs of those who liked and/or commented on the respective post. Our collected dataset consists of more than 15 million interactions.

For the purpose of this study, we made use of friends' lists and interactions, and we want to make use of the remaining data for future studies. Facebook employs a number of distinct friendship recommendation algorithms, all of which are geared toward fostering new connections. One of them is called the friends-of-friends (*fof*) algorithm, and its purpose is to locate and promote friendship relationships that are easily accepted. This is because the algorithm searches for and suggests users who are already known to or are already familiar with the platform. This is extremely important for friending algorithms

since people have a strong tendency to avoid developing relationship connections with unknown individuals. Our model employs the *fof* algorithm to detect interactive friends, whereas Facebook's algorithm for finding friends of friends finds friends who are already known to the user.

Figure 2 illustrates how the proposed model determines the existence of interacting linkages. In this scenario, Users A, R, S, E, and M are friends of both the target user (*x*) and the *fof*. If user *x* interacts with friends with whom user *fof* also interacts, then it is likely that users *x* and *fof* will interact with one another if the target interacts with friends with whom user *fof* also interacts. This strategy is predicated on the idea that if two people interact with content that was posted by the same set of mutual friends, then it is highly probable that those users will interact with the content that was posted by the other person. The Facebook Friends of Friends method operates under the presumption that if two users have friends in common, then it is highly likely that they are acquainted with one another.

Fig. 2. Interactive friends-of-friends sub-graph example.

B. Experimental Setting

The recommendations for interactive buddies are going to be generated by the proposed model. The acquired dataset from Facebook included the posts that users made, and for each post, we collected a list of all the user IDs of people who liked the relevant posts and interacted with them. In addition to that, we additionally retrieved a list of the user IDs of everyone who had commented on the relevant post. On Facebook, the most prevalent forms of interaction are liking and commenting posts. It's arguable that a user's likes and comments are more accurate reflections of their character than what they say about themselves on their Facebook pages which include a variety of interests and activities. According to the findings of our investigation, therefore, likes and comments are indicators of interacting friends. Figure 3 shows the ways in which the data for our model have been prepared:

User ID	Friend ID	# of Interactions
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Fig. 3. Data labels.

To determine the total number of interactions that took place between two users (the user and the friend), we added up all the likes and comments that were passed back and forth between them. When preprocessing the dataset, users who had fewer than three explicit interactions were removed from consideration. There have been a total of 386480 interactions, and a total of 6426 individuals that have engaged in conversation with 8638 friends. Cross-validation was utilized in order to fine-tune the model’s hyperparameters. In addition, the number of interactions was brought down to a single level. The unknown interactions that occurred between users during the course of the experiment were shuffled around and given a random order 10 times across the 10 separate iterations of the experiment that we conducted. When reporting the results of the error rate calculation, the mean of all 10 runs was used. In terms of the train-test split, we segmented our dataset so that 90% of it would be used for training, while the remaining 10% would be concealed for testing.

C. Evaluation Metrics

RMSE is the measure that we utilized in order to evaluate how accurate the proposed strategy was. The error rate of the model is computed by adding up all of the discrepancies that exist between the interactions that are expected to take place between Facebook users and the actual interactions that are used in the test set. The values were squared to remove any negative integers and rooted to retrieve the actual information for each user.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{|T|} \sum_{(i,j) \in T} (r'_{ij} - r_{ij})^2} \tag{1}$$

where T denotes the total number of users, while i and j stand in for the user and the friend, respectively. r'_{ij} and r_{ij} denote the anticipated and actual interactions between user i and friend j , respectively.

Figure 4 demonstrates that the performance of the proposed model is superior to that of the baseline MF [26, 27]. As can be seen in Figure 5, the training error rate begins to decrease, as anticipated, after the first epoch. During our experiment, we determined that the optimal number of epochs to use was 10, given that the error rate remained constant beyond that point.

Fig. 4. A comparison of the test RMSE performance between the proposed PMF and baseline MF.

D. Instances of Recommendation Results

We give six specific instances of random target users who have a high number of active users as friends, a mid-range number of active users as friends, and a low number of active users as friends in order to keep things brief. Tables I-VI display the performance of the model in predicting interactive friends for the target users. In Tables I and II, the model reports that the target users 1037 and 289 each have 197 and 181 interactive friends, respectively. It also predicts that the recommended friends will interact with the target users between 8.7 and 10.9 times. The highest expected number of interactions between target users and their recommended interactive friends is reduced when target users engage less frequently with their own friends. According to the data shown in Tables III and IV, the target users have 33 and 44 interactive friends, respectively, and the model expectation for the number of interactions is between 3.25 and 5.19 times.

Fig. 5. PMF performance in the training process using RMSE.

TABLE I. EXAMPLE 1 OF HIGHLY ACTIVE TARGET USER

User ID	# of interactive friends	Friend ID	# of predicted interactions
1037	197	16644	10.9
		104649	9.9
		37163	9.8
		50525	9.7
		979710	9.2
		248304	9.0
		235852	8.9
		84052	8.8
		711283	8.5
682540	8.1		

TABLE II. EXAMPLE 2 OF HIGHLY ACTIVE TARGET USER

User ID	# of interactive friends	Friend ID	# of predicted interactions
289	181 friends	2016	11.3
		41538	10.6
		378726	9.6
		328142	9.4
		720814	9.1
		896432	8.7
		246978	8.7
		19361	8.7
		5361	8.6
		83995	8.6

TABLE III. EXAMPLE 1 OF MID-ACTIVE TARGET USER

User ID	# of interactive friends	Friend ID	# of predicted interactions
15354	33 friends	16520	5.1
		13460	4.8
		6363	4.8
		381593	4.8
		242746	4.7
		5878	4.6
		83907	4.6
		4828	4.6
		1380564	4.6
499184	4.5		

TABLE IV. EXAMPLE 2 OF MID-ACTIVE TARGET USER

User ID	# of interactive friends	Friend ID	# of predicted interactions
411568	44 friends	66577	3.9
		5770	3.5
		254107	3.5
		41538	3.4
		13208	3.4
		295620	3.4
		370432	3.3
		65770	3.3
		59526	3.3
28966	3.2		

TABLE V. EXAMPLE 1 OF LOW-ACTIVE TARGET USER

User ID	# of interactive friends	Friend ID	# of predicted interactions
178741	7 friends	247287	2.3
		238092	1.8
		95127	1.7
		484116	1.7
		201396	1.6
		896574	1.6
		24869	1.6
		56805	1.6
		43996	1.6
257436	1.6		

TABLE VI. EXAMPLE 2 OF LOW-ACTIVE TARGET USERS

User ID	# of interactive friends	Friend ID	# of predicted interactions
94606	2 friends	335330	1.3
		56105	1.3
		199802	1.3
		7561	1.2
		94935	1.2
		1587350	1.1
		46648	1.1
		284747	1.0
		395289	1.0
373383	1.0		

Tables V and VI provide examples of a low-target user who has only 2 friends who connect with each other, and the model predicted only 1 to 1.4 times as many interactions between the target user and his or her suggested friends. In conclusion, the performance of the proposed model when applied to the dataset obtained from Facebook depended on the engagement of the user. If the target user is already friends with a large number of highly interactive people, the model will suggest additional

highly interactive people who are not currently friends with the target user. The same principle applies to users who are members of interaction groups in the middle and lower classes.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, our goal was to find a solution to the sparsity problem, which occurs when there are insufficient explicit facts and makes it difficult to recommend new friends with a level of accuracy that is considered acceptable. In this paper, we focused our efforts on the goal of building a recommendation model using a probabilistic approach to the matrix factorization method.

This method leverages the known side information in our Facebook dataset, which is the explicit interactions between users, such as likes to posts, comments, and so on, and predicts the unknown interactions between non-friend users, therefore suggesting new friendships that are expected to be accepted. Our dataset is an actual one that was crawled from Facebook, preprocessed, and then added to the model. It was demonstrated that the proposed model performed better than the baseline model and was successful in predicting more accurate suggestions. In addition, our model was successful in predicting strong interactions between the target user and a true hidden friend. In the future, we are interested in including additional supplementary data, such as a user's preferred movies, books, music, etc., in order to improve the precision of the model and to produce explanations for the recommendations. This, in turn, will undoubtedly result in an improvement in the level of satisfaction experienced by users who utilize the system.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Burke, "Hybrid Web Recommender Systems," in *The Adaptive Web*, vol. 4321, P. Brusilovsky, A. Kobsa, and W. Nejdl, Eds. New York, NY, USA: Springer, 2007, pp. 377–408.
- [2] P. Resnick, N. Iacovou, M. Suchak, P. Bergstrom, and J. Riedl, "GroupLens: an open architecture for collaborative filtering of netnews," in *ACM conference on Computer supported cooperative work*, North Carolina, USA, Oct. 1994, pp. 175–186, <https://doi.org/10.1145/192844.192905>.
- [3] G. Linden, B. Smith, and J. York, "Amazon.com recommendations: item-to-item collaborative filtering," *IEEE Internet Computing*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 76–80, Jan. 2003, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MIC.2003.1167344>.
- [4] F. Ricci, "Recommender Systems: Models and Techniques," in *Encyclopedia of Social Network Analysis and Mining*, New York, NY, USA: Springer, 2014, pp. 1511–1522.
- [5] P. Melville, R. J. Mooney, and R. Nagarajan, "Content-boosted collaborative filtering for improved recommendations," in *Eighteenth National Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, Alberta, Canada, Aug. 2002, pp. 187–192.
- [6] M. J. Pazzani and D. Billsus, "Content-based recommendation systems," in *The adaptive web: methods and strategies of web personalization*, Berlin, Germany: Springer, 2007, pp. 325–341.
- [7] V. Rohilla, M. Kaur, and S. Chakraborty, "An Empirical Framework for Recommendation-based Location Services Using Deep Learning," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 9186–9191, Oct. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5126>.
- [8] A. M. Rashid, G. Karypis, and J. Riedl, "Learning preferences of new users in recommender systems: an information theoretic approach," *ACM SIGKDD Explorations Newsletter*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 90–100, Sep. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1145/1540276.1540302>.
- [9] S. R. Gopi and M. Karthikeyan, "Effectiveness of Crop Recommendation and Yield Prediction using Hybrid Moth Flame

- Optimization with Machine Learning," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 11360–11365, Aug. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.6092>.
- [10] R. Salakhutdinov and A. Mnih, "Probabilistic Matrix Factorization," in *20th International Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems*, Vancouver, BC, Canada, Dec. 2007, pp. 1257–1264.
- [11] Y. Dong, S. Fang, K. Jiang, F. Chen, and G. Yin, "Probabilistic Matrix Factorization Recommendation Algorithm with User Trust Similarity," *MATEC Web of Conferences*, vol. 208, 2018, Art. no. 05004, <https://doi.org/10.1051/mateconf/201820805004>.
- [12] J. M. Hernandez-Lobato, N. Houlsby, and Z. Ghahramani, "Probabilistic Matrix Factorization with Non-random Missing Data," in *31st International Conference on Machine Learning*, Beijing, China, Jun. 2014, pp. 1512–1520.
- [13] N. Fusi, R. Sheth, and M. Elibol, "Probabilistic Matrix Factorization for Automated Machine Learning," in *32nd Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems*, Montreal, QC, Canada, 2018, vol. 31, pp. 1–10.
- [14] J. Liu, C. Wu, Y. Xiong, and W. Liu, "List-wise probabilistic matrix factorization for recommendation," *Information Sciences*, vol. 278, pp. 434–447, Sep. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2014.03.063>.
- [15] M. Alshammari, O. Nasraoui, and S. Sanders, "Mining Semantic Knowledge Graphs to Add Explainability to Black Box Recommender Systems," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 110563–110579, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2934633>.
- [16] T. Zhou, H. Shan, A. Banerjee, and G. Sapiro, "Kernelized Probabilistic Matrix Factorization: Exploiting Graphs and Side Information," in *12th SIAM International Conference on Data Mining*, Anaheim, CA, USA, Apr. 2012, pp. 403–414, <https://doi.org/10.1137/1.9781611972825.35>.
- [17] K. Li, X. Zhou, F. Lin, W. Zeng, and G. Alterovitz, "Deep Probabilistic Matrix Factorization Framework for Online Collaborative Filtering," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 56117–56128, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2900698>.
- [18] K. P. Murphy, *Probabilistic Machine Learning: An Introduction*. Cambridge, MA, United States: MIT Press, 2022.
- [19] Z. Xuan, J. Li, J. Yu, X. Feng, B. Zhao, and L. Wang, "A Probabilistic Matrix Factorization Method for Identifying lncRNA-Disease Associations," *Genes*, vol. 10, no. 2, Feb. 2019, Art. no. 126, <https://doi.org/10.3390/genes10020126>.
- [20] J. Yang, Z. Li, X. Fan, and Y. Cheng, "Drug–Disease Association and Drug-Relocation Predictions in Complex Diseases Using Causal Inference–Probabilistic Matrix Factorization," *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, vol. 54, no. 9, pp. 2562–2569, Sep. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ci500340n>.
- [21] Z. Li, J. Liu, X. Zhu, T. Liu, and H. Lu, "Image annotation using multi-correlation probabilistic matrix factorization," in *18th ACM international Conference on Multimedia*, Florence, Italy, Oct. 2010, pp. 1187–1190, <https://doi.org/10.1145/1873951.1874183>.
- [22] W. Zhang, F. Liu, D. Xu, and L. Jiang, "Recommendation system in social networks with topical attention and probabilistic matrix factorization," *PLOS ONE*, vol. 14, no. 10, Sep. 2019, Art. no. e0223967, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0223967>.
- [23] H. Ma, H. Yang, M. R. Lyu, and I. King, "SoRec: social recommendation using probabilistic matrix factorization," in *17th ACM conference on Information and knowledge management*, Napa, CA, USA, Oct. 2008, pp. 931–940, <https://doi.org/10.1145/1458082.1458205>.
- [24] B. Jiang, Z. Lu, N. Li, J. Wu, and Z. Jiang, "Retweet Prediction Using Social-Aware Probabilistic Matrix Factorization," in *18th International Conference on Computational Science*, Wuxi, China, Jun. 2018, pp. 316–327, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-93698-7_24.
- [25] D. M. S. Alshammari, "FacebookPMF," May 24, 2023, Accessed: Sep. 21, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/drmohammedsanad/FacebookPMF>.
- [26] Z. Liu and H. Zhong, "Study on Tag, Trust and Probability Matrix Factorization Based Social Network Recommendation," *KSII Transactions on Internet and Information Systems*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 2082–2102, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.3837/tiis.2018.05.010>.
- [27] M. Mahyoub, J. Algaraady, M. Alrahali, and A. Alblwi, "Sentiment Analysis of Public Tweets Towards the Emergence of SARS-CoV-2 Omicron Variant: A Social Media Analytics Framework," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 8525–8531, Jun. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4865>.
- [28] M. Alshammari and A. Alshammari, "Friend Recommendation Engine for Facebook Users via Collaborative Filtering," *International Journal of Computers Communications & Control*, vol. 18, no. 2, Apr. 2023, Art. no. 4998, <https://doi.org/10.15837/ijccc.2023.2.4998>.
- [29] Y. Koren, R. Bell, and C. Volinsky, "Matrix Factorization Techniques for Recommender Systems," *Computer*, vol. 42, no. 8, pp. 30–37, Dec. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MC.2009.263>.

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Inconel 625 Coatings on AISI 304 Steel using Laser Cladding: Microstructure and Hardness

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ABSTRACT

Nickel-base super alloys such as Inconel 625 are preferred in high-temperature and corrosive environments. Since Inconel 625 is expensive and often difficult to machine, it is advantageous to deposit a protective coating of this alloy on a less costly and easily machinable substrate material such as stainless steel. In the present work, coatings were produced on AISI 304 steel substrate by depositing Inconel 625 powder using the laser cladding technique. As-received powder particles of Inconel 625 alloy were characterized using X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) and Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FESEM). After laser cladding, it becomes important to carry out the microstructural analysis of the cross-sectional areas of the coating and the substrate/coating interface region, for further understanding of the structure-property correlations. In this study, the microstructural features of the coatings and substrate/coating interface were examined using an FESEM equipped with X-ray elemental analysis. The phase analysis of the coating was carried out using XRD. In the coating region, the growth of planar, cellular, columnar dendritic, and equiaxed grains was noticed. It was observed that small amounts of Laves phase were precipitated. Furthermore, the laser-clad Inconel 625 coating showed superior microhardness over the stainless steel substrate.

Keywords-laser cladding; Inconel 625; super alloy; AISI 304; microstructure; microhardness

I. INTRODUCTION

Various industrial applications demand joining of dissimilar materials. Coatings of superalloys onto austenitic stainless steels find relevance in chemical process plants, oil, and gas industries [1]. Functional materials play a crucial role by imparting a range of properties to material components. These properties cannot be achieved through a single material alone, especially for long-lasting requirements [2]. Conventional coating methods such as surface welding and plasma spraying exhibit a few shortcomings. These techniques are slow, tough to automate, labor intensive, and require more heat input [3]. High heat input leads to problems such as distortion, embrittlement, and dimensional instability. On the other hand, additive manufacturing techniques are popular nowadays. Laser cladding is one such technique which imparts lower levels of dilution and distortion [4]. In the laser cladding technique, a laser beam melts both the additive material and a thin layer of the substrate, ensuring a metallurgical bonding

between them. The additive alloy may be introduced in-situ into the interaction zone of the laser beam and the substrate, either in wire or in powder form. In recent years, a few studies have been conducted to investigate the laser cladding of superalloy coatings on stainless steel base. Authors in [5] compared the performances of a Nd:YAG laser and a Yb:YAG monomode fiber laser source by generating the cladding tracks of cobalt-base superalloy on AISI 304 stainless steel substrate. Authors in [6] explored how varying laser metal deposition parameters, including focal length, frequency, and scanning speed, influence the characteristics of cobalt-base superalloy deposited onto precipitation-hardened martensitic stainless steel. Authors in [7] noted that the quality of the cladding layer is contingent on the following factors, ranked in decreasing order of significance: scanning speed, power, and overlapping rate. Authors in [8-10] studied the dry friction, wear, and high temperature oxidation behavior of the laser cladding coatings produced using feedstock powders of nickel-base and cobalt-base superalloys onto a cold rolled stainless steel substrate.

Authors in [11] developed a laser cladded surface by using preplaced TiC powder which produced a remarkable increase in hardness and wear resistance in the cladded region. Authors in [12] evaluated the optimum laser processing parameters for deposition of defect-free cobalt-base superalloy cladding layer with suitable geometry (width, height, undulation, and dilution) on austenitic stainless steel. Authors in [13] implemented an online monitoring system to observe the rapid heating and cooling rates occurring during the laser cladding of nickel-base superalloy onto AISI 304 austenitic steel.

Limited literature exists about microstructural and mechanical investigations of superalloy layers fabricated via laser cladding on stainless steel substrate. The present work deals with the deposition of Inconel 625 powder, a nickel-base superalloy, on AISI 304 stainless steel using the laser cladding technique. This paper describes the clad layer microstructure, phase composition, and microhardness as functions of position. The findings from this study are pivotal for advancing the investigation into the viability of Inconel 625 claddings on stainless steel piston rings, aiming to improve their longevity.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the present study, AISI 304 austenitic stainless steel substrates with 10 mm diameter and 25 mm thickness were prepared for depositing the clads. Prior to the cladding process, the substrate surface was polished with sandpaper and cleaned with acetone to eliminate stains and other contaminants. A commercial, inert gas atomized Inconel 625 powder was used as the feedstock material for laser cladding. The nominal chemical composition of the substrate and the feedstock powder is given in Table I. Figure 1(a) displays the Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FESEM) image of the as-received Inconel 625 powder. It was observed that the majority of the powder particles were spherical in shape. However, few particles had small satellites attached. Image analysis of secondary electron micrographs revealed that the average size of the powder particle was approximately 70.4 μm (Figure 1(b)).

TABLE I. CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF AISI 304 STEEL AND INCONEL 625 POWDER

Element (wt. %)	C	Si	Cr	Mn	Nb	Mo	Ni	Fe
AISI 304	0.05	0.4	20.01	1.17			7.97	70.4
Inconel 625	0.03	0.35	22.5	0.4	3.9	7.92	62.4	2.5

Laser cladding process was performed using an Yb-fiber laser system (IPG YLS-4000). The power and scanning velocity of the continuous wave laser beam were set at 1.5 kW and 10 mm/s, respectively. The diameter of the laser beam was fixed at 2.5 mm. During the cladding process, to provide a protective atmosphere, Argon gas was used with an injection rate of 18 l/min. The system utilized a coaxial type powder feeder nozzle. Clad powder was deposited onto the substrate at a feed rate of 360 mg/s. Argon was also utilized as powder carrier gas. Figure 2(a) shows the laser powder deposition system and the specimen setup. The entire arrangement was connected to a Computer Numerical Control (CNC) platform to achieve precision coating. The powder focus was 17 mm beneath the nozzle tip. The bidirectional scanning pattern was

adopted with constant offset distance. The coaxial nozzle and the cladding procedure can be better understood with the help of the schematic diagram given in Figure 2(b). A homogeneous powder stream was ensured by the coaxial nozzle. Figure 2(c) shows the clad coated sample. The clad coating thickness achieved was about 1.6 mm using single-layer powder deposition with a 40% overlapping ratio. The average surface roughness of the laser-cladded surface was measured to be 28.3 μm .

Fig. 1. Inconel 625 superalloy powder: (a) FESEM image, (b) particle size distribution estimated using the ImageJ software.

The laser cladded sample was sectioned using wire electric discharge machining to examine the evolution of microstructure along the coating depth. The cut section was polished with sandpapers down to 3000 grit size, followed by final polishing with a velvet cloth with alumina powder and diamond paste. The polished sample was chemically etched in aqua regia solution (3 ml HCl and 1 ml HNO₃) for 30 s. The microstructural morphology, as well as the elemental composition of the clad coatings were analyzed using a FEI Quanta FEG 250 field emission scanning electron microscope equipped with an Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS). A Bruker D8 Advance X-ray diffractometer was used in order to identify the phases present in the clad samples. The X-ray wavelength was 1.5406 \AA using a Cu target source, while the scanning speed and step size were 2.8°/minute and 0.02°, respectively. A microhardness tester, Chennai Metco Economet VH-1 MDX, was utilized to obtain a Vickers microhardness profile along the cross section of the cladded sample. A load of 0.3 kg and a dwell time of 15 s were considered.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Microstructure and Phase Analysis

The interaction between the laser beam, the additive alloy, and the substrate material results in complex metallurgical and solidification processes. The process variables such as laser

power, beam spot size, laser scanning velocity, laser beam absorption, and powder feed rate decide the temperature distributions in the melt pool. Within the melt pool, high temperature gradients induce intense convection due to the Marangoni effect [14, 15]. According to the Marangoni flow, the flow velocity is higher at the edge of the melt pool than that at the center. Also, the flow velocity at the bottom of the melt pool is higher than that at the top. The Marangoni effect leads to rapid homogenization of the melt. The cooling rates are very high during the laser cladding process due to which solid-state diffusive transformations are usually inhibited. Therefore, microstructural evolution is dependent on the solidification rate (R) and temperature gradient at the solid-liquid interface (G) [16].

Fig. 2. Laser cladding process: (a) experimental arrangement, (b) schematic diagram of the coaxial powder deposition system, and (c) a laser clad sample.

Figure 3 shows the secondary electron images of the laser clad layer and the interface region. The various grain morphology transformations observed throughout the cross-sectional area of the coating are due to the combined effects of G and R. This could be elucidated with the help of the solidification behavior of the melt pool [17]. While the ratio G/R governs the morphology preference of solidification structure, the product $G \times R$, termed as cooling rate, decides the solidification microstructure size. From Figure 3, it is observed that the solidification began by epitaxial growth on the substrate. Due to the high value of G/R (constitutional undercooling criterion) at the bottom of the melt pool, few planar crystals appeared firstly, as shown in Figure 3(b). The

formation of the region of plane fine grains indicated that the metallurgical bonding between the substrate and the clad layer is of high strength [18]. Cracks or pores have not been found in the coating/substrate interface. With the solidification progression, the value of G/R decreased. Simultaneously, the cooling rate increased from zero at bottom of the layer to a maximum value at the top of the coating. As the solid/liquid interface shifted, the solidification structure changed from planar to cellular (Figure 3(b)) on account of the decreasing G and the enhancing R. In the middle zone of the coating, further reduction of G resulted in columnar dendritic structure (with primary and secondary dendritic arms) along the direction of G, as shown in Figure 3(c). Due to the very low G and the increased degree of constitutional supercooling, the solidification mode transitioned to equiaxed grains in the top zone of the coating, as displayed in Figure 3(d).

Fig. 3. FESEM images of a laser clad sample: (a) cross-sectional, (b) coating/substrate interface zone, (c) middle, and (d) top zone of coating.

Figure 4 shows the EDS spot analysis results at different locations on the specimen cross-section. Figure 5 depicts the EDS elemental distribution maps near the clad/substrate interface.

Fig. 4. FESEM-EDS spot analyses of a laser cladded sample: (a) clad region near the interface, (b) interface, (c) substrate.

Fig. 5. EDS mappings around the clad/substrate interface: (a) existing elements, (b) Fe, (c) Ni.

It can be seen from Figure 4(c) that the Fe, Cr, and Ni contents in the substrate are consistent with the nominal composition of AISI 304 steel (see Table I). The Fe content in the coating (58.4 wt. % for white fusion zone and 50 wt.% for the clad region near the interface) increased significantly when compared with that of the additive alloy (2.5 wt.%), due to the dilution of Fe from the substrate into the coating. It is to be noted that the bulk composition of the substrate is Fe. Increase

in Fe concentration in the transition region between the cladding layer and the substrate can be seen in Figure 5(b). The concentration of Ni is diminished in the region where Fe is enriched, as seen in Figures 4(a), 4(b), and 5(c). Similar observations were reported in [19].

Figure 6 displays the XRD patterns of the Inconel 625 powder and the Inconel 625 laser coating. For both samples, the major XRD peaks can be noticed at $2\theta = 43.6^\circ, 50.6^\circ,$ and 74.6° . These are very comparable to the peak positions of pure Ni, as available from the JCPDS standard, present at $2\theta = 44.5^\circ, 51.9^\circ,$ and 76.4° . Alloying and other trace elements in the solid solution of Inconel 625 affected the inter-planar spacing of the fcc-Ni present in the Inconel 625 [20]. Consequently, a slight difference occurred between the peak positions of pure Ni and the XRD peak positions of the Inconel 625.

Fig. 6. XRD spectra of Inconel 625 powder and the laser cladded coating. L denotes the Laves phase.

Fig. 7. (a) FESEM image showing Laves phases in the cladding layer, (b) EDS analysis of Laves phase, (c) EDS analysis of coating matrix phase.

As is evident from Figure 6, the Laves phase structure also appeared in the laser clad layer. However, the presence of the Laves phase was limited to a small region of the clad layer. Figure 7(a) shows the FESEM image of the Laves phases. The results of the EDS analysis revealed that the Laves phase contained more concentrations of Nb and Mo elements, and lesser Ni, Cr, and Fe elements (see Figure 7(b)) than the coating matrix phase (Figure 7(c)). Due to the reduced solid solubility of Mo and Nb elements in the fcc-Ni matrix, these alloying elements were rejected into the bulk liquid. During the solidification process, microsegregation of Nb and Mo into the interdendritic region resulted in the formation of Laves phases [21, 22]. The brittle nature of the Laves phase is detrimental to the mechanical properties [23].

B. Microhardness

Figure 9 shows the Vickers microhardness values along the cross-section of cladding layer and substrate. Hardness is significantly increased from 174 HV_{0.3} to 256 HV_{0.3} when traversed from the substrate to the top layer of the coating. The microhardness depth profile can be divided into three regions: cladding zone, Fe dilution zone, and substrate (Figure 8). The high hardness of the Inconel 625 cladding zone is attributed to the solid solution strengthening of the matrix phase by elements such as Mo and Nb. A small fraction of the secondary precipitates, i.e. the Laves phase, present in the interdendritic regions is also responsible for the high hardness values. The enhanced hardness at the top layer of the clad exists due to the fine equiaxed grains, which were evolved by higher cooling rate due to the direct exposure to the surrounding air. The decrease in microhardness in the Fe dilution zone is attributed to the element composition change due to the diffusion of iron by partial dilution from substrate to coating. The clad hardness decreases with increasing Fe dilution [24].

Fig. 8. Vickers microhardness profile obtained for the Inconel 625 laser clad sample.

IV. CONCLUSION

In the present work, defect-free laser cladding coatings were fabricated on the surface of AISI 304 stainless steel samples using Inconel 625 powder deposition. The solidification microstructures, compositions, phases formed, and microhardness of the coating and bonding regions were investigated. Laser cladding exhibited a good metallurgical

bonding between the substrate and the coating. The morphology of the grains varied from the bonding region to the top layer of the clad in the following fashion: planar, cellular, columnar dendritic, and equiaxed crystals. At the bottom region of coating, Fe dilution from the substrate to the coating was found. The indexing of diffraction pattern of Inconel 625 clad coatings showed that the coating consisted primarily of γ -Ni phase. The existence of a small Laves phase fraction was also detected. A maximum in microhardness appeared at the top zone of the clad coating, which is about 1.5 times higher than that of the stainless steel substrate. This indicates that the coated cladding sample may effectively resist the abrasive wear.

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REFERENCES

- [1] M. A. Derakhshi, J. Kangazian, and M. Shamanian, "Electron beam welding of inconel 617 to AISI 310: Corrosion behavior of weld metal," *Vacuum*, vol. 161, pp. 371–374, Mar. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vacuum.2019.01.005>.
- [2] M. Ramadan, "Interface Structure and Elements Diffusion of As-Cast and Annealed Ductile Iron/Stainless Steel Bimetal Castings," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 2709–2714, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1856>.
- [3] A. S. C. M. D'Oliveira, P. S. C. P. da Silva, and R. M. C. Vilar, "Microstructural features of consecutive layers of Stellite 6 deposited by laser cladding," *Surface and Coatings Technology*, vol. 153, no. 2, pp. 203–209, Apr. 2002, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0257-8972\(01\)01687-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0257-8972(01)01687-5).
- [4] J. C. Heigel, P. Michaleris, and T. A. Palmer, "In situ monitoring and characterization of distortion during laser cladding of Inconel® 625," *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, vol. 220, pp. 135–145, Jun. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2014.12.029>.
- [5] J. del Val *et al.*, "Laser cladding of Co-based superalloy coatings: Comparative study between Nd:YAG laser and fibre laser," *Surface and Coatings Technology*, vol. 204, no. 12, pp. 1957–1961, Mar. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surfcoat.2009.11.036>.
- [6] A. E. Pilehrood, A. Mashhuriazar, A. H. Baghdadi, Z. Sajuri, and H. Omidvar, "Effect of Laser Metal Deposition Parameters on the Characteristics of Stellite 6 Deposited Layers on Precipitation-Hardened Stainless Steel," *Materials*, vol. 14, no. 19, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 5662, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma14195662>.
- [7] Y. T. Xu, W. J. Zhao, T. D. Xia, and X. J. Wang, "Study of Laser Cladding Novel Co-9Al-7.5W Superalloy on 304 Stainless Steel," *Advanced Materials Research*, vol. 291–294, pp. 872–877, 2011, <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMR.291-294.872>.
- [8] J. Pereira, J. Zambrano, M. Licausi, M. Tobar, and V. Amigó, "Tribology and high temperature friction wear behavior of MCrAlY laser cladding coatings on stainless steel," *Wear*, vol. 330–331, pp. 280–287, May 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wear.2015.01.048>.
- [9] J. C. Pereira, J. C. Zambrano, M. J. Tobar, A. Yañez, and V. Amigó, "High temperature oxidation behavior of laser cladding MCrAlY coatings on austenitic stainless steel," *Surface and Coatings Technology*, vol. 270, pp. 243–248, May 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surfcoat.2015.02.050>.
- [10] N. Jeyaprakash, C.-H. Yang, and S. Sivasankaran, "Laser cladding process of Cobalt and Nickel based hard-micron-layers on 316L-stainless-steel-substrate," *Materials and Manufacturing Processes*, vol. 35, no. 2, pp. 142–151, Jan. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10426914.2019.1692354>.

- [11] E. R. I. Mahmoud and H. F. El-Labban, "Microstructure and Wear Behavior of TiC Coating Deposited on Spheroidized Graphite Cast Iron Using Laser Surfacing," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 4, no. 5, pp. 696–701, Oct. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.483>.
- [12] M. T. Veiga, G. O. Verran, A. Rabelo, M. F. Teixeira, P. R. A. Bloemer, and L. J. da Silva, "Laser cladding of a cobalt-based superalloy on austenitic stainless steel," *Soldagem e Inspecao*, vol. 26, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1590/0104-9224/SI26.02>.
- [13] G. Muvvala, D. Patra Karmakar, and A. K. Nath, "Online monitoring of thermo-cycles and its correlation with microstructure in laser cladding of nickel based super alloy," *Optics and Lasers in Engineering*, vol. 88, pp. 139–152, Jan. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.optlaseng.2016.08.005>.
- [14] C. Li, Y. Xu, T. Jia, J. Zhao, and X. Han, "Numerical simulation research on multifield coupling evolution mechanism of IN625 laser cladding on nodular cast iron," *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, vol. 119, no. 9, pp. 5647–5669, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00170-021-08249-y>.
- [15] K. Touileb, R. Djoudjou, and A. Ouis, "Effect of Viscosity on the GTA Welds Bead Penetration in Relation with Surface Tension Elements," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 952–955, Apr. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.643>.
- [16] N. A. Berjeza, S. P. Velikevitch, V. I. Mazhukin, I. Smurov, and G. Flamant, "Influence of temperature gradient to solidification velocity ratio on the structure transformation in pulsed- and CW-laser surface treatment," *Applied Surface Science*, vol. 86, no. 1, pp. 303–309, Feb. 1995, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-4332\(94\)00446-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-4332(94)00446-3).
- [17] B. Fotovvati, S. F. Wayne, G. Lewis, and E. Asadi, "A Review on Melt-Pool Characteristics in Laser Welding of Metals," *Advances in Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 2018, Apr. 2018, Art. no. e4920718, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/4920718>.
- [18] M. Xiaoli, W. Kaiming, F. Hanguang, J. Jiang, L. Yongping, and Y. Dawei, "Effect of mo Content on Microstructure and Properties of Laser Cladding Fe-BASED Alloy Coatings," *Surface Review and Letters*, vol. 25, pp. 1850077–168, Jan. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0218625X18500774>.
- [19] K. Feng *et al.*, "Improved high-temperature hardness and wear resistance of Inconel 625 coatings fabricated by laser cladding," *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, vol. 243, pp. 82–91, May 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2016.12.001>.
- [20] T. E. Abioye, D. G. McCartney, and A. T. Clare, "Laser cladding of Inconel 625 wire for corrosion protection," *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, vol. 217, pp. 232–240, Mar. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2014.10.024>.
- [21] D. Deng, in *Additively Manufactured Inconel 718: Microstructures and Mechanical Properties*, Linköping, Sweden: Linköping University Electronic Press, 2018, pp. 12–13.
- [22] S. G. K. Manikandan, D. Sivakumar, K. Prasad Rao, and M. Kamaraj, "Laves phase in alloy 718 fusion zone — microscopic and calorimetric studies," *Materials Characterization*, vol. 100, pp. 192–206, Feb. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchar.2014.11.035>.
- [23] S. Antonov *et al.*, "The effect of phosphorus on the formation of grain boundary laves phase in high-refractory content Ni-based superalloys," *Scripta Materialia*, vol. 161, pp. 44–48, Mar. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scriptamat.2018.10.015>.
- [24] S. Zanzarin, S. Bengtsson, and A. Molinari, "Study of dilution in laser cladding of a carbon steel substrate with Co alloy powders," *Powder Metallurgy*, vol. 59, no. 1, pp. 85–94, Jan. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00325899.2015.1118842>.

A Novel Framework to Strengthen Early Warning Systems

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ABSTRACT

The impact of disasters on the population and environment is an important research area. Multiple criteria need to be analyzed while making policy decisions in order to control the effect of a disaster. Researchers have used many variants of the Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS), a Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) method for prioritizing the alternatives. Additionally, the detrimental effects of disasters have compelled stakeholders to proactively prepare by strengthening crucial key elements of an Early Warning System (EWS) so that timely alerts can be produced. In this paper, a Disaster Information Provider (DIP) framework is proposed, which employs a TOPSIS variant to bolster weak elements of a people-centric EWS. Governments may utilize delivered rankings to strengthen the weak elements of the EWS in an affected area. Extensive experimentation proves the usability of the DIP framework for strengthening EWS.

Keywords-MCDM; TOPSIS; disaster management; EWS

I. INTRODUCTION

Disasters severely impact an area, often beyond its response capacity, leading to environmental impact and considerable loss of human life and property [1]. To contain the spread and considerably reduce the impact of disasters, there is a need for an upgraded Early Warning System (EWS) [2].

A. Background and Motivation

In 2020, use of multi-hazard EWSs successfully protected human life in 23 UN countries with a success rate of 93.63% [2], which proves their relevance and appropriateness. Communities, local organizations, and governments utilize EWSs to assess the risk and warn people in advance so that timely action could be taken [3]. Authors in [4] developed an EWS to mitigate the overall morbidity and mortality rates. Authors in [5] reviewed existing EWS methodologies for real time identification of at-risk patients in hospitals. Authors in [6] advocated the expansion of EWS for better forecasting and anticipatory action. The World Meteorological Organization recently employed Impact Based Forecasting (IBF), which creates warnings highlighting potential implications of a climate related threat in addition to providing weather

information [7]. Authors in [8] suggested a low cost EWS to the people residing in nearby wildlife areas to resolve human-wildlife conflicts [8]. Governments all over the world look for different ways to strengthen their respective EWSs. Driven by this objective, we propose a novel method to strengthen people-centric EWS for better disaster preparedness in the future.

B. Contribution

In 2020, Data Knowledge Group (DKG) provided a COVID-19 Regional Safety Assessment Analytical Framework [9]. It ranked 200 affected regions emphasizing on monitoring 6 criteria (quarantine efficiency, government efficiency of risk management, monitoring and detection, health readiness, regional resilience, and emergency preparedness). Such monitoring enables the government to lay out strategic plans for disaster preparedness. Motivated by this, we propose a novel Disaster Information Provider (DIP) framework. The ranking provided by DIP signals the disaster readiness of a region in comparison to other regions. This knowledge can be used by weaker regions (having lower ranking) to prepare against future disasters of a similar nature more effectively. Extensive experimentation was carried out to study the effectiveness of the proposed DIP framework.

B. Weight Analyzer

The four DMs corresponding to each key element of the EWS serve as input to the Weight Analyzer for computing the weights of the sub-criteria. These weights are used to construct 4 weighted DMs which serve as input to the Ranking Unit. The weight Analyzer computes sub-criteria weights using the entropy metric (see (1a), (1b)). Literature suggests that entropy-based weights methods are better than others because they avoid RRP [24].

$$V_j = -\frac{1}{\log m} \sum_{i=1}^m \frac{X_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^m X_{ij}} \log \frac{X_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^m X_{ij}} \quad (1a)$$

$$R_j = \frac{1-V_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n (1-V_j)} \quad (1b)$$

where R_j indicates the resilience (weight) of m regions on sub-criterion j , such that $\sum_{j=1}^n R_j = 1$, V_j indicates the vulnerability (entropy) of m regions on sub-criterion j , $0 \leq V_j \leq 1$, and X_{ij} is the performance value of region i on the sub-criterion j .

C. Ranking Unit

The Ranking Unit (Figure 2) deploys a novel TOPSIS variant, for ranking the regions considering the past performance of regions along with current performance of regions during catastrophes. It is executed in three phases, with two inputs, decision matrix $[X]$ and weight W_j , for each sub-criterion j , to output the rank of regions obtained as per the score of TOPSIS variant. For each EWS element, a region with low rank is implied to have outstanding disaster preparedness for that element.

Phase I starts with the normalization of the input DM $[X]$ using max-linear normalization to avoid RRP [24]. Subsequently, the weights (resilience) of the sub-criteria are multiplied with $[X]$ to obtain the performance of each region DM $[Y]$ with respect to the overall performance of DIP on each sub-criterion. Phase II computes two separation vectors namely a hypothetically best (S^+) and worst (S^-) solution set [25] to identify the best solution which is not only closest to the best possible solution, but also the farthest from the worst possible solution [20]. In order to get the hypothetical best solution S^+ , the maximum value for the benefit criterion Y_j^+ and the minimum value for the cost criterion Y_j^- from m regions are considered. Similarly, the hypothetical worst solution S^- corresponds to negative ideal (worst) criteria values in $[Y]$ where benefit criterion Y_j^+ takes the lowest value while the cost criterion Y_j^- takes the highest. Further, separation vectors S_i^+ and S_i^- are obtained for each region i from its corresponding positive and negative ideal solutions respectively. Euclidean distance is used for the calculation of the separation vectors due to its popularity and simplicity over other distance measures [25, 26]. The computed separation vectors for each region i are used in phase III, to decide their ranking based on their distance from the optimized ideal reference point O . It is found that irregularities occur in traditional TOPSIS due to calculations of positive and negative ideal solutions using relative distance measure [27]. Instead of calculating the relative closeness to the positive ideal solution, the Ranking Unit obtains the absolute closeness to the positive ideal solution (C_i^+) and the

absolute farness from the negative ideal solution (F_i^-) for each region i . The idea is to get a solution that is closest to the ideal reference point O , so that the absolute rank score A_i for each region i is the closest to the positive ideal reference point and the farthest from the negative ideal reference point. The smaller the value of A_i , the closer is C_i^+ to point O and the farther is F_i^- to point O . Thus, the regions are ranked in increasing order of A_i . The Ranking Unit is executed four times to obtain four different ranks of a region, with each rank corresponding to a unique element of the EWS. Note that non-numerical factors (qualitative scales) of EWS, if any, are converted into quantitative ones before providing the input to the Ranking Unit. A numerical example detailing the three phases of the Ranking Unit is shown in Appendix II.

```

Input:  $[X]$ : DM where  $X_{ij}$  is the performance value of region  $i$  on the sub-criterion  $j$ .  $R_j$  weights indicating the resilience of  $m$  regions on sub-criterion  $j$ , such that  $\sum_{j=1}^n R_j = 1$ 
Output: Dict  $D$  with regions ranked in increasing order of  $A_i$ .
Process of the Ranking Unit:
// Phase I: Computing Weighted Normalized DM  $[Y]$ 
// Normalizing Decision matrix  $[X]$ 
For  $X_{ij}$  in  $[X]$  do
    if  $j \in J^+$  then  $X_{ij} = \frac{X_{ij}}{X_j^{\max}}$  else  $X_{ij} = 1 - \frac{X_{ij}}{X_j^{\max}}$ 
//  $J^+$ : {set of user-specified benefit sub-criteria}
//  $J^-$ : {set of user-specified cost sub-criteria}
For each element  $X_{ij}$  in  $[X]$  do
     $Y_{ij} = R_j * X_{ij}$ 
// Phase II: Construction of Separation Vectors
// Set  $\{S^+\}$  and  $\{S^-\}$  indicates hypothetical positive and negative ideal solution for each region
For  $Y_j$  in  $[Y]$  do
    if  $j \in J^+$  then  $Y_j^+ = \max(Y_{ij})$  else  $Y_j^+ = \min(Y_{ij})$ 
     $\{S^+\} = \{S^+\} \wedge Y_j^+$ 
For  $Y_j$  in  $[Y]$  do
    if  $j \in J^-$  then  $Y_j^- = \min(Y_{ij})$  else  $Y_j^- = \max(Y_{ij})$ 
     $\{S^-\} = \{S^-\} \wedge Y_j^-$ 
// Compute Separation Vectors ( $S_i^+$  &  $S_i^-$ ) for each region
For  $Y_i$  in  $[Y]$  do
     $S_i^+ = \sum_j \sqrt{\sum (Y_{ij} - Y_j^+)^2}$ 
     $S_i^- = \sum_j \sqrt{\sum (Y_{ij} - Y_j^-)^2}$ 
// Phase III Ranking of Regions
// create empty dictionary to store regions with their corresponding score
D = {}
// Point  $O$  indicates optimized ideal reference point
Let  $O(C_p, F_N)$ ;  $C_p = \min(S^+)$  and  $F_N = \max(S^-)$ 
For each region  $i$  do
     $C_i^+ = S_i^+ - C_p$ 
     $F_i^- = S_i^- - F_N$ 
//  $C_i^+$  is the absolute closeness of region  $i$  to positive ideal solution
//  $F_i^-$  is the absolute farness metric of region  $i$  to negative ideal solution
     $A_i = \sqrt{[C_i^+]^2 + [F_i^-]^2}$ 
//  $A_i$  is the score of the region  $i$  considering its closeness and farness from ideal solution
    D.update( $i, A_i$ )
Sort the dictionary D in increasing order of scores.

```

Fig. 2. Rankin Unit pseudo code.

III. EXPERIMENTAL PART

In order to demonstrate the utility of the novel DIP framework, we used Python 3 for coding and DKG report for the dataset [9]. Usability of DIP framework is initially shown by testing the efficacy of the Sub-Criteria Analyzer in sub-section A, followed by validating the performance of the Ranking Unit in sub-section B. The ranks obtained by the proposed DIP framework are discussed in sub-section C. We intend to work on sensitivity analysis in the future for signifying the use of vulnerability and resilience in the Weight Analyzer.

A. Efficacy of the Sub-Criteria Analyzer using EWS Criteria

The Sub-Criteria Analyzer allocates 34 sub-criteria [9] as per the definition of the four key elements of the people-centric EWS [22]. This allocation resulted into three DMs, each corresponding to a component of the EWS representing performance value. In each matrix, a row represents a region and a column indicates a sub-criterion. Each cell in the matrix shows the performance value of a sub criterion for a region (alternative). Mapping of sub-criteria is detailed in Appendix I.

Nine sub-criteria were categorized under the RK class, reflecting prior knowledge of the risk faced by the communities, with 6 of them as benefit sub-criteria and 3 as cost sub-criteria. Seven fall under the MWS class emphasizing on technical monitoring and warning services in the disaster-prone region. Considering the economic stability of the disaster affected region, 2 sub-criteria were classified as cost whereas 5 were taken as benefit sub-criteria. The rest of the 17 sub-criteria relate to the preparedness and the capability of the communities to cope up with disaster in the affected regions, so they were classified under the RC class of the EWS. Four were used as cost and 13 as benefit sub-criteria. In the absence of a direct association of any of the given 34 sub-criteria with the DC element, this element is not used while ranking. The Ranking Unit of the DIP framework is executed for each of the performance matrices to obtain rankings of all regions at level 1. Hence, each region is assigned 3 ranks, where the rank of a particular region reflects the performance of the region with respect to a particular key element of the EWS. Ranks for regions at level 2, 3 and 4 are not calculated due to the unavailability of data in the DKG report.

The 3 ranks for each region obtained by the Ranking Unit were aggregated for comparing the efficacy of the Sub-Criteria Analyzer with that of the DKG categorization. The Spearman rank correlation of the aggregated ranks was computed with that of DKG rank. In order to validate the efficacy of the Sub-Criteria Analyzer, the obtained results were compared with those of the DKG-TOPSIS (see Table I). Further, the average Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Root Mean Squared error (RMSE) were computed to measure the net error score for each of the three key elements. The EWS-TOPSIS method was found to perform slightly better, clearly indicating that the ranking reported in the DKG report was preserved when the Sub-Criteria Analyzer allocated sub-criteria using the EWS categorization. Lower values of the metrics for EWS-TOPSIS confirm the enhanced performance of the Sub-Criteria Analyzer deploying EWS categorization. We recommend the

use of RMSE in strengthening EWS as it is more sensitive to outliers leading to avoidance of large errors in predicted scores.

TABLE I. COMPARISON OF SUB-CRITERIA ANALYZER WRT DKG-TOPSIS AND EWS-TOPSIS

Error Value/ Rank Correlation	DKG-TOPSIS	EWS-TOPSIS
Average MAE	0.19	0.14
Average RMSE	0.22	0.09
Spearman rank correlation	0.85	0.88

B. Validating the Performance of the Ranking Unit

The ranks of the disaster affected regions at levels 1 are computed by employing 6 standard benefit criteria as mentioned in the DKG report using the Ranking Unit (RU-TOPSIS) and by using the traditional TOPSIS method (T-TOPSIS). Average MAE and RMSE were also calculated to measure the errors in the predicted scores by RU-TOPSIS and T-TOPSIS methods using the actual DKG scores along with Spearman rank correlation (Table II). Lower error values for RU-TOPSIS compared to T-TOPSIS and higher values of rank correlation vindicate the capability of the Ranking Unit in generating scores nearly close to the DKG scores. Hence, that variant of TOPSIS used in Ranking Unit seems promising for ranking disaster affected regions efficiently.

TABLE II. COMPARISON OF RANKING WITH RESPECT TO T-TOPSIS AND RU-TOPSIS

Error Value/ Rank Correlation	T-TOPSIS	RU-TOPSIS
Average MAE	0.27	0.15
Average RMSE	0.31	0.11
Spearman rank correlation	0.83	0.86

C. Discussion on the Ranks obtained by the Proposed DIP Framework

The results presented above depict that the proposed DIP framework is effective for understanding the preparedness of regions for combating similar disasters in future. The ranks obtained by DIP for regions of level I with respect to each key element of EWS are shown in Table III. Regions with higher scores compared to the DKG report should concentrate more on pre-disaster preparedness with respect to that particular key element of the EWS. Precisely, Switzerland (CH) and Israel (IL) should pay heed to all the three elements of EWS although they were ranked first in the DKG framework. Improved ranks for Netherlands (NL), Saudi Arabia (SA), and Vietnam (VN) compared to DKG ranks reveal better preparedness and hence, must pursue existing strategies to excel further. Countries like Canada (CA), Denmark (DK), New Zealand (HU), and Singapore (SG) should re-evaluate the strategies to strengthen the RC element of EWS. The line graph plotted in Figure 3 uses the scores computed by the components for better visualization of the preparedness as per the EWS framework. It is visible that most of the countries, excluding China (CH) and Vietnam (VN), are aware of RK. However, all except Austria (AT) fallback on MWS criteria. Intermediate scores for RC reveal further strengthening of the adopted strategies for combating the disaster by all countries, excluding Japan (JP) and Korea (KA).

TABLE III. REGION RANKS AS PER KEY ELEMENTS OF EWS

Region	Rank				Region	Rank			
	DKG	RK	MWS	RC		DKG	RK	MWS	RC
AU	8	6	15	14	NL	19	13	11	17
AT	6	8	1	13	NZ	9	12	3	15
CA	12	10	10	16	NO	14	11	18	18
CN	7	19	9	5	SA	17	16	17	11
DK	15	7	12	20	SG	4	3	2	8
DE	2	1	19	3	KR	10	9	20	4
HK	13	17	4	6	CH	1	5	8	2
HU	18	14	14	19	TW	16	18	7	9
IL	3	4		7	AE	11	15	13	10
JP	5	2	6	1	VN	20	20	16	12

Australia (AU), Austria (AT), Canada (CA), China (CN), Denmark (DK), Germany (DE), Hong Kong (HK), Hungary (HU), Israel (IL), Japan (JP), Netherlands (NL), New Zealand (NZ), Norway (NO), Saudi Arabia (SA), Singapore (SG), South Korea (KR), Switzerland (CH), Taiwan (TW), United Arab Emirates (AE), Vietnam (VN)

Fig. 3. Comparison of the scores obtained by the three key elements of the EWS.

IV. CONCLUSION

To better train governments to fight disasters like COVID-19 there is a need to reinforce key elements of a people-centric Early Warning System (EWS). Inspired by this, the authors propose a Disaster Information Provider (DIP) framework with the goal of ranking disaster-affected regions based on their past performance under the key elements of the EWS. The obtained ranking provided by DIP identifies weak elements of EWS in a specific region, allowing policymakers to plan more operative tactical strategies to fight future pandemics. The proposed DIP framework is a stand-alone model and can work for different disasters by modifying the input data to the Sub-Criteria Analyzer, such as reducing the risk accompanying with cyclones and sidestepping the probable damages due to tsunamis.

APPENDIX I

TABLE IV. CATEGORIZATION OF SUB-CRITERIA UNDER KEY ELEMENTS OF EWS

Criteria/ Sub-Criteria		Description
Type	Name	
Risk Knowledge: RK		
RK ₁	Geopolitical vulnerabilities	Region's political instability based on its economic & military strength.
RK ₂	Economic sustainability	Region's capacity to remain economically sustainable after pandemic.
RK ₃	Previous national	Emergencies focusing on preparation

	emergency experience	policies and government-led emergency relief efforts.
RK ₄	Societal emergency resilience	Resilience, preparedness, past history, psychological/cultural/religious attitudes.
RK ₅	Chronic diseases	Geographic risk in terms of proximity to infection prone areas, # border crossings, number of # population dense areas.
RK ₆	Infection spread risk	Number of citizens prone to risk of getting infected with covid.
RK ₇	Level of modern sanitization methods	Poor sanitization higher risk
RK ₈	Covid-19 equipment availability	Total and per capita emergency equipment stockpiles.
RK ₉	Epidemiology system level of development	Epidemiology system of a region in terms of quantity, distribution and sophistication.
Monitoring and Warning Service: MWS		
MWS ₁	Monitoring & disaster management	Sophisticated surveillance and monitoring technologies.
MWS ₂	Government surveillance technology	Monitoring infection rate & compliance with quarantine measures.
MWS ₃	Reliability and transparency of data	Reliability of reported statistics.
MWS ₄	Scope of diagnostic methods	Diverse diagnostic techniques and their effectiveness
MWS ₅	AI for diagnostics and prognostics	Usage of AI analysis of results reducing the manpower needed.
MWS ₆	Scale of quarantine	Lockdown/social distancing.
MWS ₇	Quarantine timeline	How early quarantine measures are taken.
Response Capability: RC		
RC ₁	Economic and supply chain freezing	Freeze via lockdown.
RC ₂	Travel restrictions	Restrictions on citizens and tourists.
RC ₃	Economic support for quarantines	Support for citizen's capacity to stay at home.
RC ₄	Criminal penalties for violating quarantine	Presence and severity of region's criminal penalties for violation.
RC ₅	Mobilization of new healthcare resources	Region's preparedness to mobilize additional healthcare resources.
RC ₆	Quantity and quality of medical staff	Education and expertise
RC ₇	Level of healthcare progressiveness	Quality of medical treatment
RC ₈	Level of technological advancement	Sophistication/modernization/effectiveness of healthcare system.
RC ₉	Testing efficiency	Time of testing and availability of lab personnel
RC ₁₀	Culture specifics and societal discipline	Cultural and societal focus on health and sanitization
RC ₁₁	Demography	Vulnerable demographics
RC ₁₂	Level of security and defense advancement	To neutralize external threat
RC ₁₃	Legislative efficiency	Deploying emergency response legislation (law)
RC ₁₄	Rapid emergency mobilization	Capacity to mobilize emergency response
RC ₁₅	Emergency military mobilization experience	Past experience of mobilizing military
RC ₁₆	Efficiency of government structure	Effective governance to identify risk-prone regions
RC ₁₇	Surveillance capabilities	Scale, scope and sophistication of surveillance capabilities.

* Considered as Cost in order to take care of the economic situation of a region.
 ** Considered as Cost as these activities may cause havoc among the people of a region.

APPENDIX II

Illustration of HU-TOPSIS on MWS Elements of EWS

Table V shows two inputs for the MWS element of EWS, namely the decision matrix [X] taken from the DKG report [9] and the sub-criterion weight (R_j). Note that weights are calculated using (1b). In Phase I, the weight of each criterion (R_j) is multiplied with the corresponding normalized values of [X] to obtain the weighted normalized decision matrix [Y], shown in the same table. In Phase II, positive (S⁺) and negative (S⁻) ideal solutions are obtained and the values are shown as the last two rows in Table V. Subsequently, for each region, positive and negative separation distances (S_i⁺ and S_i⁻) are computed with respect to the ideal solutions (S⁺, S⁻), which are plotted in Figure 4. Here, the values of S_i⁺ and S_i⁻ are plotted on the y-axis for all the regions plotted on the x-axis. It clearly shows that S_{AT}⁺ attains minimum value among all the regions (shown in blue color). Also, S_{AT}⁻ attains maximum value among all the regions (shown in red color). Hence, Austria is closest to its positive ideal solution S_{AU}⁺ and farthest from its negative ideal solution S_{AU}⁻. So, it should be given rank 1. Likewise, S_{KR}⁺ gets maximum value among all the regions

(shown in blue color) and S_{KR}⁻ gets minimum value among all the regions (shown in red color), thereby making South Korea (KR) the farthest from its positive ideal solution and the closest to its negative ideal solution. So, it should be given the last rank. It is difficult to find the rank for regions like IL (Israel) and JP (Japan) by simply visualizing the graph in Figure 4. So, we move to phase III. On execution of RU-TOPSIS on level 1 regions, score A_i obtained is shown in Figure 5 with the corresponding ranks shown in red squares.

Fig. 4. Plot of S_i⁺ and S_i⁻ obtained by RU-TOPSIS.

TABLE V. INPUT FOR THE RANKING UNIT AS PER THE MWS ELEMENTS OF THE EWS

Region	MWS ₁	MWS ₂	MWS ₃	MWS ₄	MWS ₅	MWS ₆	MWS ₇
AU	18	1	8.5	0.5	11.33	0.65	15
AT	18	1	8.5	0.5	11.33	0.65	15
CA	18	1	17	1	11.33	0.65	15
CN	12	0.6	17	1	11.33	0.65	15
DK	18	1	12.75	0.75	11.33	0.65	15
DE	18	1	13.6	0.8	17	0.98	15
HK	18	1	17	1	17.33	1	15
HU	18	1	8.5	0.5	11.33	0.65	15
IL	18	1	15.98	0.94	17	0.98	15
JP	18	1	15.3	0.9	17	0.98	15
NL	18	1	17	1	11.33	0.65	15
NZ	18	1	12.75	0.75	11.33	0.65	15
NO	18	1	8.5	0.5	11.33	0.65	15
SA	18	1	8.5	0.5	11.33	0.65	15
SG	18	1	14.96	0.88	17	0.98	15
KR	18	1	14.17	0.83	11.33	0.65	15
CH	18	1	9.18	0.54	17	0.98	15
TW	18	1	13.6	0.8	11.33	0.65	15
AE	18	1	13.6	0.8	8.5	0.49	15
VN	18	1	8.5	0.5	11.33	0.65	15
R _j	0.015846	0.180596	0.116155	6.88E-15	6.88E-15	0.036619	0.650784
{S ⁺ }	0.015846	0.180596	0.116155	6.88E-15	6.88E-15	0	0
{S ⁻ }	0.010564	0.090298	0.056972	6.88E-15	6.88E-15	0.015069	0.650784

Fig. 5. RU-TOPSIS scores and ranks for level 1 regions for the MWS criteria of an EWS.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. J. Winter, "Disaster? No surprise," *Environmental Politics*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 70–88, Jan. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09644016.2020.1865726>.
- [2] M. Esposito, L. Palma, A. Belli, L. Sabbatini, and P. Pierleoni, "Recent Advances in Internet of Things Solutions for Early Warning Systems: A Review," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 6, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 2124, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22062124>.
- [3] "Early warning system | UNDRR," Aug. 30, 2007. <http://www.undrr.org/terminology/early-warning-system>.
- [4] T. Kelhe, C. Jain, M. Bhandarkar, and A. Deshpande, "A Smart Early Warning System for Disease Outbreak with a Case Study of COVID-19 in India," in *IEEE Pune Section International Conference*, Pune, India, Dec. 2020, pp. 113–118, <https://doi.org/10.1109/PuneCon50868.2020.9362380>.

- [5] A. H. S. Fang, W. T. Lim, and T. Balakrishnan, "Early warning score validation methodologies and performance metrics: a systematic review," *BMC Medical Informatics and Decision Making*, vol. 20, no. 1, Jun. 2020, Art. no. 111, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12911-020-01144-8>.
- [6] T. D. G. Hermans, R. Sakic Trogrlic, M. J. C. van den Homberg, H. Bailon, R. Sarku, and A. Mosurska, "Exploring the integration of local and scientific knowledge in early warning systems for disaster risk reduction: a review," *Natural Hazards*, vol. 114, no. 2, pp. 1125–1152, Nov. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-022-05468-8>.
- [7] W. Wang, T. Zhang, T. Yao, and B. An, "Monitoring and early warning system of Cirenmaco glacial lake in the central Himalayas," *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, vol. 73, Apr. 2022, Art. no. 102914, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2022.102914>.
- [8] E. K. Ronoh, S. Mirau, and M. A. Dida, "Human-Wildlife Conflict Early Warning System Using the Internet of Things and Short Message Service," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 8273–8277, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4662>.
- [9] DKG 2020, "COVID-19 Regional Safety Assessment." <https://analytics.dkv.global/covid-regional-assessment-200-regions/full-report.pdf>.
- [10] EWC III, "Developing Early Warning Systems: A Checklist," in *Third International Conference on Early Warning*, Bonn, Germany, Mar. 2006.
- [11] M. F. Abdullah, S. Siraj, and R. E. Hodgett, "An Overview of Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) Application in Managing Water-Related Disaster Events: Analyzing 20 Years of Literature for Flood and Drought Events," *Water*, vol. 13, no. 10, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 1358, <https://doi.org/10.3390/w13101358>.
- [12] M. E. Banihabib, F.-S. Hashemi-Madani, and A. Forghani, "Comparison of Compensatory and non-Compensatory Multi Criteria Decision Making Models in Water Resources Strategic Management," *Water Resources Management*, vol. 31, no. 12, pp. 3745–3759, Sep. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11269-017-1702-x>.
- [13] E. S. Saleh and A. M. Kimiagari, "Ranking Tehran's Stock Exchange Top Fifty Stocks Using Fundamental Indexes and Fuzzy TOPSIS," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 1863–1869, Aug. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1252>.
- [14] M. Mousavi, I. Ghazi, and B. Omarae, "Risk Assessment in the Maritime Industry," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1377–1381, Feb. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.836>.
- [15] N. Benmoussa, A. Elyamami, K. Mansouri, M. Qbadou, and E. Illoussamen, "A Multi-Criteria Decision Making Approach for Enhancing University Accreditation Process," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 3726–3733, Feb. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2352>.
- [16] A. R. Radhi and A. M. Burhan, "Non-Profit Organization Project Selection Process Using the Hygiene Method of Multi-Criteria Decision Making," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 9097–9101, Oct. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5175>.
- [17] K. R. Ramakrishnan and S. Chakraborty, "A cloud TOPSIS model for green supplier selection," *Facta Universitatis, Series: Mechanical Engineering*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 375–397, Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.22190/FUME200307036R>.
- [18] U. Rahardja, N. Lutfiani, S. Sudaryono, and R. Rochmawati, "The Strategy of Enhancing Employee Reward Using TOPSIS Method as a Decision Support System," *Indonesian Journal of Computing and Cybernetics Systems*, vol. 14, no. 4, pp. 387–396, Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.22146/ijccs.58298>.
- [19] B. Yang, J. Zhao, and H. Zhao, "A robust method for avoiding rank reversal in the TOPSIS," *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, vol. 174, Dec. 2022, Art. no. 108776, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2022.108776>.
- [20] S. Hezer, E. Gelmez, and E. Ozceylan, "Comparative analysis of TOPSIS, VIKOR and COPRAS methods for the COVID-19 Regional Safety Assessment," *Journal of Infection and Public Health*, vol. 14, no. 6, pp. 775–786, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jiph.2021.03.003>.
- [21] H. Maleki and S. Zahir, "A Comprehensive Literature Review of the Rank Reversal Phenomenon in the Analytic Hierarchy Process," *Journal of Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis*, vol. 20, no. 3–4, pp. 141–155, 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1002/mcda.1479>.
- [22] WMO, "Multi-hazard Early Warning Systems: A Checklist," in *Outcome of the first Multi-hazard Early Warning Conference*, Cancun, Mexico, Dec. 2017, pp. 1–20.
- [23] D. Baneres, M. E. Rodriguez, A. E. Guerrero-Roldan, and A. Karadeniz, "An Early Warning System to Detect At-Risk Students in Online Higher Education," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 10, no. 13, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 4427, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10134427>.
- [24] R. F. de F. Aires and L. Ferreira, "The rank reversal problem in multi-criteria decision making: A literature review," *Pesquisa Operacional*, vol. 38, no. 2, pp. 331–362, Aug. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1590/0101-7438.2018.038.02.0331>.
- [25] P. Talukdar and P. Dutta, "A Comparative Study of TOPSIS Method via Different Distance Measure," *International Journal of Research in Advent Technology*, vol. 7, no. 5, pp. 118–126, Jun. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.32622/ijrat.75201937>.
- [26] R. F. de F. Aires and L. Ferreira, "A new approach to avoid rank reversal cases in the TOPSIS method," *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, vol. 132, pp. 84–97, Jun. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2019.04.023>.
- [27] W. Yang, "Ingenious Solution for the Rank Reversal Problem of TOPSIS Method," *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, vol. 2020, Jan. 2020, Art. no. e9676518, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/9676518>.

Photocatalytic and Magnetic Properties of TiO₂ Micro- and Nano- Powders decorated by Magnetic Cocatalysts

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, photocatalytic TiO₂ micro- and nano-powders coated by Ni and Co nanoclusters were prepared by the original electroless deposition method. The magnetic properties of Ni and Co nanoclusters decorating TiO₂ grains were studied by the magnetometry measurements of the temperature dependence of magnetization. Their optical spectroscopy measurements showed a significant increase in light absorption by Ni and Co coated TiO₂ nanopowders. The photocatalytic properties of the obtained magnetic nanopowders were studied with Electron Paramagnetic Resonance spectroscopy as well.

Keywords-titanium dioxide; photocatalysis; magnetic clusters; magnetometry; optical spectrometry

I. INTRODUCTION

Hydrogen is a very attractive clean energy source. The use of hydrogen as an energy source has several advantages, such as good energy conversion effectiveness, ability to be produced from water with zero emissions, and different storage options. The product of hydrogen combustion is water and therefore produces no pollutants. The sun's energy can split water into hydrogen and oxygen in the presence of catalysts in a reaction

called photocatalysis. Photocatalytic water splitting using semiconducting catalysts has received much attention and is a subject of active research. One of the most promising semiconductor photocatalysts is TiO₂ due to properties such as high photocatalytic activity, excellent incident photoelectric conversion efficiency, photostability, chemical stability, corrosion resistance, low price and nontoxicity [1-5]. The photocatalytic reaction proceeds as follows. Absorbed into

TiO₂, which is a semiconductor and has an energy gap of 3.2 eV between the valence and conduction bands, a sunlight photon with suitable energy creates an electron-hole pair. Having reached the TiO₂ surface, the produced electron and holes interact with water molecules and cause their splitting into hydrogen and oxygen [6].

As mentioned above, the photocatalytic reaction occurs on the surface. Therefore, the photocatalysts are usually used in the form of powders in order to increase the surface area. Therefore, photocatalytic nanopowders are characterized by higher activity than photocatalytic thin films [7]. However, in this case, another problem emerges: on the surface of small particles, the annihilation of electron-hole pairs is very fast, and they have no time to participate in the reaction. The high recombination rate of photogenerated electron and hole pairs in TiO₂ reduces quantum yield and photocatalytic activity, respectively. To circumvent the fast electron-hole annihilation, cocatalyst clusters of various substances are deposited on the TiO₂ grain surface. The clusters capture electrons and holes and hinder their annihilation. This process is schematically illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Electron-hole pair production in the cluster-deposited particles of TiO₂/Ni powder under the effect of sunlight quanta and their interaction with surrounding molecules.

In this paper, we are exploring ways to improve the photocatalytic properties of TiO₂ through the coating of TiO₂ nanoparticles by various metal clusters using the results of [8-10] and some recent experiments. First of all, the preparation and characterization of Ni and Co coated TiO₂ nanoparticles will be described and their magnetic properties and photocatalytic activity under UV-V will be investigated. The main contribution of the current paper is in the development of a new, low-temperature chemical technology for the deposition of magnetic nanosized cocatalysts on the surfaces of TiO₂ nanoparticles. A simultaneous study of the superparamagnetic and optical properties of these magnetic photocatalytic nanocomplexes and the determination of the influence of oxygen vacancies on these properties is also a contribution. It should be noted that if we compare the existing literature data, the influence of oxygen vacancies was specifically studied, but for another photocatalyst, ZnO, and only partially, since the optical absorption spectra were not studied [11].

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

TiO₂ nanopowders coated by Ni clusters were obtained by a novel technology of metallic cluster deposition on a fine TiO₂ nanopowder with a mean grain size of 25 nm (Degussa AG) developed at the Andronikashvili Institute of Physics of Ivane Javakhishvili Tbilisi State University. The technology is

electroless and inexpensive. It proceeds at low temperatures (50-60°C) and hence does not lead to changes of the physical properties of the material to be coated nor of the material of clusters [12-14].

The composition of the chemical solution for obtaining of TiO₂/Ni nanopowder is: NiSO₄·6H₂O 30 g/l that provides the Ni ions, KNaC₄H₄O₆·4H₂O - 40 g/l is a complexing agent preventing the excess of free metal ions concentration, ethylenediamine-15 g/l is a cross-linker, and NaOH - 40 g/l, regenerative borohydride NaBH₄-6 g/l. The excess amount of borohydride causes the solution to decay and the precipitation of metallic Ni in the solution. At the end of the process, the solution is transparent, which confirms the precipitation of the bulk of the nickel from the solution. The same method was applied for the preparation of TiO₂/Co powders: an aqueous cobalt solution containing: CoSO₄·7H₂O - 5 g/L, C₁₀H₁₆N₂O₈ (ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid, EDTA, Trilon B) - 35 g/L, NaOH - 40 g/L (giving a pH of 13 after TiO₂ addition), NaBH₄ was added (in aqueous solution to give a concentration of 0.5-5 g/L) after suspending the TiO₂ (0.5 g per 100 mL solution) in the solution. Thereafter the suspension was treated by ultrasound for 20 min and then stirred by a magnetic bar during heating (75-80°C). The amount of borohydride and the duration of the reaction determine the quantity of the deposited cobalt. The decorated particles were separated from the solution by centrifuging and were dried in the air. The characteristics of the chemicals used are given in Table I.

TABLE I. PURITY OF THE CHEMICALS USED FROM MANUFACTURER WITHOUT ADDITIONAL PURIFICATION

Name	Purity	Manufacturer
TiO ₂ anatase, 44 μm	99%	Sigma-Aldrich
TiO ₂ anatase, 30nm	99.98%	Us-nano
TiO ₂ anatase, 5-10 nm	99%	Sun-nano
P 25, 30-35 nm	99%	Degussa
NiSO ₄ × 6H ₂ O	98.5%	Sigma-Aldrich
NaBH ₄	99%	Sigma-Aldrich
NaOH	99%	Sigma-Aldrich
KNaC ₄ H ₄ O ₆ ·4H ₂ O	99.18%	JSC Base No. 1 of Chemical Reactives
CoSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	99%	Sigma-Aldrich
Ethylenediamine EDTA	99%	Sigma-Aldrich

The concentration of the suspensions used in the optical studies was 5 mg of powder per 600 ml of distillate. It was observed in the experiments that the ratio of light absorption by suspensions to scattering depends on the concentration of the suspension, and it is maximal for suspensions with a concentration of about 5/600 mg/ml. That is why suspensions of the mentioned concentration were used in the experiments in order to make the absorption peaks shown on the absorption curves sharper.

Magnetization measurements were carried out using a Vibrating Sample Magnetometer - VSM (Cryogenic Limited, UK) allowing one to do magnetization measurements in a wide range of temperature 1.7 ÷ 293 K and in Zero-magnetic Field Cooling (ZFC) and magnetic Field Cooling (FC) modes. At ZFC mode, a sample is first cooled down to 1.7 K in a zero magnetic field and then the sample is heated in a small magnetic field up to room temperature. Measurements are

taken to obtain the sample-blocking temperature T_B related to the magnetic anisotropy of the nanoparticles. The application of an external field introduces the competition between the spin orientation along the magnetic anisotropy axis and the direction of the magnetic field under the action of thermal fluctuations. Small applied fields (≤ 500 Oe) are generally insufficient to induce spin reorientation away from the anisotropy axis at low temperature, with increasing temperature, however, thermal activation assists in the orientation of the magnetic moments into the direction of the magnetic field magnetizing a sample. The recorded magnetization passes through a maximum before it is reduced again at higher temperatures due to thermally induced reversals of the particle magnetization vectors according to the Curie law in the superparamagnetic magnetic state above the blocking temperature T_B . Due to the laboriousness of VSM measurements, the homemade Radio-Frequency (RF) resonant magnetometer (RF RM) was also used to characterize the magnetic properties of the received samples, allowing one to carry out more easily and quickly assess of the magnetic state (ferromagnetic, superparamagnetic) of the tested sample compared to the comparatively long-term measurements by the VSM magnetometry [15]. The circuit based on the LC resonance generator (Figures 2-3) is used for the measurements of the transverse susceptibility of magnetic samples.

Fig. 2. Circuit based on the LC resonance generator.

Fig. 3. LC generator circuit scheme.

The sample was placed into the induction coil of the LC generator. The variations of its resonance frequency were measured at the variations in the external magnetic field H_{DC} , which was perpendicular to the coil field H_{RF} . The standard representation of the frequency of the LC generator oscillations is:

$$f = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{LC}} \quad (1)$$

where L is the coil inductance and C is its capacity.

The introduction of the sample into the induction coil changed the inductance value by ΔL . If $\Delta L/L \ll 1$, by differentiating this equation, we get:

$$\frac{\Delta f}{f} = -\frac{\Delta L}{2L} \quad (2)$$

The inductance variations are connected with the changes in the magnetic susceptibility of the studied magnetic nanopowders. The semiconductor powder coated with metallic clusters obtained by the electroless method is placed in the capsule and the magnetic characteristics are measured using the above methods. Then optical and EPR measurements are performed.

The optical absorption spectra of the distillate suspensions of the photocatalyst powders were measured. First, the light absorption of the distilled water over the entire working spectral range was studied and appeared to be rather low. However, in order to exclude the distortion of the absorption spectra of the powders under study as a result of the distillate effect, we recorded the absorption spectra of the powders dissolved in the distillate in reference to the pure distillate. For this aim, a cell with a suspension of the powder under study was placed in one compartment of the spectrophotometer F-46 and an identical cell with pure distillate in another compartment. To check the validity of the procedure, we prepared several similar reference aqueous suspensions of the same powder. Then their absorption curves were taken. The obtained spectra coincided very closely with a maximum difference of $\pm 5\%$. EPR spectra were recorded by spectrometer EPR-V (Russia), with 9.1 GHz microwave frequency and 100 KHz magnetic field modulation frequency. Experiments were carried out with microwave power of 15 mW. As an EPR standard, MgO doped with Mn^{2+} ions was used. The values of hyperfine splitting and g-factor were measured by means of EPR standard.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Magnetic and Photocatalytic Properties of the Ni-coated TiO_2 Nanopowders

The results of VSM magnetization measurements for two types of TiO_2/Ni nanopowders obtained as a result of TiO_2 nanopowder coating for 10 and 1 min are presented in Figures 4-8.

Fig. 4. Temperature dependence of the zero-field-cooled (ZFC) and field-cooled (FC) magnetic moments of the anatase TiO_2 nanopowder coated by Ni clusters. Deposition time: 10 min. Applied magnetic field: 1000 Oe.

Fig. 5. Temperature dependence of the ZFC magnetic moment of the anatase TiO_2 nanopowder coated by Ni clusters with deposition time of 1 min in applied magnetic field of 1000 Oe.

Fig. 6. Hysteresis loop for the anatase TiO_2 nanopowder coated by Ni nanoclusters for 10 min at $T=260$ K.

The results of the VSM measurements are confirmed by the RF RM measurements (Figure 7). Absence of hysteresis at up-and-down scanning of the magnetic field is observed, indicating that deposited nickel clusters are superparamagnetic. By making appropriate measurements at nitrogen temperature, it is easy to establish whether below $T=77$ K or above this temperature the blocking temperature T_B of the superparamagnetic coating is located. Figures 7 and 8 show the possibility of controlling the magnetization of nanoclusters by the RF RM method depending on the duration of the reduction reaction and the concentration of the reducing agent.

Fig. 7. RF resonant magnetometer frequency f change Δf dependence ($f=7$ MHz at $H=0$) at room temperature on the magnetic field strength (\bullet) and (\times) mark up and down magnetic field sweeps) for: 1 – Ni coated anatase TiO_2 , reaction duration 10 min and 2 – Ni coated anatase TiO_2 , reaction duration 30 s.

Fig. 8. Dependence of the frequency deviation Δf of the RF resonant magnetometer on the magnitude of the external magnetic field depending on the concentration of the reducing agent: 1 – TiO_2/Ni , reducing agent concentration 3 g/l and 2 – TiO_2/Ni , reducing agent concentration 1 g/l.

The characteristic features of the magnetization data in Figures 4 and 5 are the peaks on the ZFC magnetic moment temperature dependences. Such peaks are known to be characteristic for the superparamagnetic particles and were observed in order to obtain the blocking temperatures of the samples to characterize the magnetic anisotropy of the particles [16]. Therefore, we conclude that the obtained nanopowders become superparamagnetic due to the presence of Ni clusters on the surface of TiO_2/Ni nanopowders. From the position of the ZFC peaks at 1000 G the blocking temperatures T_B are about 9 and 6 K, respectively. The superparamagnetic behavior of samples can also be seen from the curves in Figure 7 due to the absence of hysteresis. In the case of low signal intensity when measuring with the RF RM method, the more sensitive EPR method [9] can be used.

For testing the efficiency of the developed nanotechnology of deposition of Ni clusters on photocatalytic TiO_2 nanopowders, we took two modifications of the TiO_2 powder, anatase and rutile, with grains of ~ 30 nm in size. We prepared their identical suspensions in distillate and recorded their absorption spectra over the wavelength range from 300 to 800 nm. Then we deposited Ni clusters on the powders under study and recorded again their absorption spectra over the same wavelength range by the same technique. Figure 9 shows the results of these experiments: curve 1 corresponds to the absorption spectrum of rutile modification of the TiO_2 powder before deposition of clusters, after deposition of clusters the spectrum hardly changed and it is omitted. Curve 2 corresponds to the absorption spectrum of the anatase modification of the TiO_2 powder before the deposition of clusters, and curve 3 to that after the deposition of the clusters. Curves 1 and 2 showed that the absorption spectra of the rutile and anatase modifications before the deposition of Ni clusters were very much alike, without any particular absorption at any wavelength. After the deposition of the clusters, the absorption spectrum of the rutile modification did not change, as was mentioned above, but the spectrum of the anatase modification changed dramatically, as curve 3 showed. The observed phenomenon is apparently caused by the fact that, before the deposition of clusters, the electron-hole pairs recombine fast on the nanoparticle surfaces, but, after the deposition of clusters, they capture the electrons and hinder the recombination. As a result, in the process of photocatalysis the number of split

water molecules increases, improving the efficiency of the photocatalytic reaction. The results on the dependence of the TiO₂/Ni nanopowder absorption spectra on the Ni deposition time are presented in Figure 10.

Fig. 9. Absorption spectra of TiO₂ nanopowders before and after coating with Ni clusters: 1- absorption spectra of nanopowders TiO₂ (rutile) before coating with Ni clusters, 2- absorption spectra of nanopowders TiO₂ (anatase) before coating with Ni clusters, 3- absorption spectra of nanopowders TiO₂ (anatase) after coating with Ni clusters.

Fig. 10. TiO₂ (Anatase) nanopowder absorption spectra dependence on deposition time: 1 - pure TiO₂, 2 - TiO₂ coated with Ni for 1 min, 3 - TiO₂ coated with Ni for 10 min.

As seen from Figure 10, after some increase in absorption with deposition time, the decrease observed in the 200-500 nm wavelength range is apparently due to the increased coverage of TiO₂ nanoparticle surfaces by Ni nanoclusters. Figure 11 shows the optical absorption spectra of TiO₂ (P25) nanopowders (TiO₂ (Degussa P25)), anatase - 86%/rutile - 14%) with mean grain size of 25 nm before and after the coating by Ni nanoclusters. As can be seen from Figure 11, the optical absorption increases as a result of cluster deposition on TiO₂ (P25) nanopowder only in the short length wave interval of 200-400 nm. So, TiO₂ (P25) nanopowders with Ni nanocluster coatings should be more suitable for photocatalysis, not only because of the larger specific surface area, but also due to the higher specific efficiency of the surface. EPR study of the photocatalytic activity of TiO₂/Ni nanopowders was also carried out [8].

B. Magnetic and Photocatalytic Properties of the Co-coated TiO₂ Nanopowders

In Figure 12, the results of the VSM magnetization measurements are presented for two types of TiO₂/Co nanopowders obtained as a result of TiO₂ nanopowder coating reaction for 1 min and full reaction, respectively.

Fig. 11. The absorption spectrum changes of TiO₂ (P25) nanopowders with 25 nm particle size as a result of Ni cluster coating: 1 - TiO₂ (P25) absorption spectrum before Ni cluster coating and 2 - TiO₂ (P25) absorption spectrum after Ni cluster coating.

Fig. 12. ZFC and FC magnetization dependence on reaction duration (reducer concentration 5g/l). The applied magnetic field is 1000 Oe.

One can see an increase in the magnetization by almost 50 times and the dependence of the magnetization of the Curie law type with a small hysteresis in the temperature dependence. The annealing of a full reaction sample at 600°C completely transforms this dependence as shown in Figures 13-16.

Fig. 13. Temperature dependence of the ZFC and FC magnetic moments of the TiO₂ nanopowder coated by Co clusters after annealing at 600°C for 1 hr. The applied magnetic field is 1000 Oe.

The analysis of the obtained results and the literature shows that Curie law type magnetization dependence of samples in Figure 12, characteristic for CoO, after annealing transforms in a magnetization dependence characteristic for nanocrystalline

superparamagnetic cobalt Co with comparatively high blocking temperatures as compared with the nickel coated samples of Figures 4-5. RF RM measurements at up and down magnetic field sweeps (Figure 16) show the superparamagnetic behavior at T=300 K and ferromagnetic one at T=77 K.

Fig. 14. Hysteresis loop for the TiO₂ nanopowder coated by Co nanoclusters after the annealing at 600°C for 1 hr at T=10 K.

Fig. 15. Hysteresis loop for TiO₂ nanopowder coated by Co nanoclusters after the annealing for 1 hr at T=10 K. Coercivity is 430 Oe.

Fig. 16. RF RM measurements at up and down magnetic field sweeps at T=300 K and at T=77 K.

Cluster concentration by changing the reaction duration was controlled by the resonant sizes coated on the TiO₂ surface. It could be regulated by choosing the restoration agent magnetometer measurements. For example, Figure 17 shows a series of resonant magnetometer curves at different reaction durations, while the reducer concentration was 5 g/l. The changes in the magnetic characteristics by selecting the reducer concentration in the aqueous solution of cobalt nanoparticles were studied also, the result can be seen in Figure 18. The result was expected. As the reducer concentration increases, the thickness of the coated cluster increases and enhances their magnetization.

Fig. 17. Frequency deviation $\Delta f(H)$ for different durations of Co cluster coating (captions on curves), at reducer concentration of 5 g/l.

Fig. 18. Frequency deviation $\Delta f(H)$ ($f = 8.5$ MHz when $H = 0$) at room temperature. (•) at sweeping of the magnetic field for the three different concentrations of the reducer (3 g/l, 5 g/l, and 7 g/l) at full reaction time.

Figure 19 shows the results of EPR measurements of Co deposited TiO₂. Nanopowders are presented depending on the Co deposition time in the solution.

Fig. 19. EPR measurements of Co deposited TiO₂: (a) Co cluster, deposition time 30 s and (b) Co cluster deposition time 5 min.

At short deposition time (Figure 19) two resonances can be seen: one corresponding to oxygen vacancies ($g = 1.9650$) and one to Co nanoclusters. At long deposition time, one could see apparently a strong resonance line corresponding to the room temperature superparamagnetic state formed by Co clusters and oxygen vacancies [9]. It was found that the optimal time for Co-deposition is 20 s. It is also confirmed by the analysis of the optical absorption spectra and EPR spectra [8].

In the conducted experiments, changing the coating duration we can regulate the nanoclusters size, and consequently, the magnetic properties of the nanoparticles powders coated with clusters.

Figure 20(a) shows the optical absorption spectra of TiO₂ powder with grain size of 44 μm where curve 1 corresponds to the absorption spectrum of the TiO₂ powder without Co clusters, and curve 2 to the absorption spectrum with deposited Co clusters. As can be seen from Figure 20(a), the optical absorption only slightly increases as a result of cluster deposition. This indicates that the majority of the created electrons and holes annihilate before they reach the TiO₂ grain surface, i.e. the annihilation occurs in the powder particle volume, and hence the deposition of clusters on the surface has no significant effect. Thus, we can conclude that micron-sized powders not only have a small specific area, but also the specific efficiency (efficiency per area unit) of the surface itself is low. Therefore, the micron-sized TiO₂ powder is not an efficient photocatalyst. The nanosize Co coated TiO₂ powders can be more effective for photocatalytic applications. To check this possibility, we deposited Co clusters on nanosize (5-10 nm) TiO₂ powders.

Fig. 20. The effect of Co nanoclusters on the optical absorption spectra of TiO₂ powders with different grain sizes: (a) 44 μm and (b) 5-10 nm. Curves 1 and 2 correspond to the absorption spectrum of the TiO₂ powder without and with Co clusters, respectively.

Fig. 21. Optical spectra of commercial TiO₂ powders and the effect of nanocluster deposition. (a) 30-35 nm size commercial TiO₂ nanopowders optical spectra: 1 - anatase, 2 - P25 (86 % anatase, 16% rutile), (b) change of the optical spectrum of P25 in the result of Co cluster coating: 1 – Optical spectrum before deposition of clusters, 2 – Optical spectrum after deposition of Co clusters.

Figure 20(b) shows the optical absorption spectra of TiO₂ nanopowder with and without Co cluster coating. As can be seen by the comparison of Figures 20(a) and (b), the light absorption of TiO₂ without Co deposition in nanopowder is much smaller than in micropowder. However, the deposition of Co clusters leads to a huge increase of the light absorption in the nanopowder sample, while the effect as we have seen was

small in micropowder. The obtained results show that TiO₂ nanopowder with Co cluster coating is more suitable for photocatalysis, not only because of the larger specific surface area, but also due to the higher specific efficiency of surface compared to the micropowder.

The maximal effect of Co cluster deposition on TiO₂ nanopowders was obtained in the case of 30-35 nm size nanopowders, when the clusters were deposited not on the pure anatase modification of TiO₂, but on the anatase and rutile mixture (86% anatase, 14% rutile), called P25. Figure 21 shows the absorption spectra of anatase with 30-35 nm nanoparticles and P25 before and after the deposition of Co clusters. As a result of the deposition, curve 1 corresponds to the absorption spectrum before the Co-cluster deposition, and curve 2 - after the Co-cluster deposition. As can be clearly seen, the increase of light absorption is significant in the ultraviolet area. Thus, using a mixture of modified anatase and rutile as a starting material instead of pure anatase and depositing the powder grain surfaces by cobalt nanoclusters, it is possible to significantly increase the TiO₂ efficiency in the ultraviolet field in view of the separation of the photo-induced charges, that is the starting stage for the entire photocatalysis process.

The next step in the photocatalyst process, which requires an increase in the efficiency of oxide photocatalysts, among them TiO₂, is the use of visible light for photocatalysis. Figure 22 shows the change of optical spectrum of P25 after the deposition of Co clusters and thermal treatment in a vacuum furnace.

Fig. 22. Change of the optical spectrum of TiO₂(P25) after complex treatment. 1 – optical spectrum of the commercial P25, 2 - optical spectrum of the commercial P25 after Co-cluster deposition and vacuum thermal treatment.

Curve 1 corresponds to the optical spectrum of commercial P25 and curve 2 corresponds to the optical spectrum of P25 after the cobalt cluster deposition and vacuum thermal treatment. Thermal treatment was carried out in a vacuum furnace at 600 °C for 7 hr. As can be seen from the Figure, the absorption spectrum shifts in the visible light area, causing the improvement of using visible light during the photocatalysis process and thus increasing this efficiency. It is clear that the reason for this is the modification of the energy gap, possibly caused by the diffusion of cobalt atoms in TiO₂ nanoparticle volume and the creation of impurity levels. As recent studies indicate, the observed effect is also associated with an increase in the number of oxygen vacancies that are formed in the samples during vacuum annealing at high temperatures [17].

Thus, the complex processing of titanium dioxide nanopowders by cobalt cluster deposition and then vacuum thermal treatment can improve its photocatalytic properties.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

TiO₂ nanopowders coated with Ni and Co nanoclusters with higher light absorption and enhanced photocatalytic activity were synthesized for the first time via an original facile electroless method. Magnetization measurements demonstrated the superparamagnetic behavior of the obtained TiO₂/Ni nanopowders and TiO₂/Co nanopowders after annealing. They confirm that nanosized Ni and Co nanoclusters are deposited on the surface of TiO₂ grains. The reasons for different changes in properties of TiO₂/Ni and TiO₂/Co magnetic nanocomplexes after annealing were explained. The photocatalytic properties of TiO₂ powder were also studied with EPR spectroscopy. The nature of the dependence of the EPR spectra on the size of magnetic clusters is established. Optical spectroscopy measurements showed a significant increase of light absorption in Ni- and Co-coated TiO₂ nanopowders, mainly in the ultraviolet region. It was found that the deposition of Ni, Co nanoclusters on the TiO₂-P25 nanopowder provides the best results and the optimal deposition time was determined to be 20 s. As a result of the vacuum heat treatment, a significant increase in absorption was observed in the visible region as well. This increase should be attributed to the appearance of impurity levels in the energy spectrum of titanium oxide, which occurs as a result of the diffusion of impurity atoms from clusters in the volume of this oxide at high temperatures. It is discussed that, in accordance with our recent results, oxygen vacancies, which arise as a result of the vacuum heat treatment at high temperatures, play an important role in the observed increase in light absorption. The facile and fast method presented in the present study can be generally applied to coat different materials with transition metal nanoclusters to develop efficient sun light-driven photocatalysts.

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REFERENCES

- [1] M. Audin and M. Kaneko, *Photocatalysis*. Tokyo, Japan: Springer, 2002.
- [2] S. Peiris, H. B. de Silva, K. N. Ranasinghe, S. V. Bandara, and I. R. Perera, "Recent development and future prospects of TiO₂ photocatalysis," *Journal of the Chinese Chemical Society*, vol. 68, no. 5, pp. 738–769, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jccs.202000465>.
- [3] R. M. Navarro, F. del Valle, J. A. Villoria de la Mano, M. C. Álvarez-Galván, and J. L. G. Fierro, "Photocatalytic Water Splitting Under Visible Light: Concept and Catalysts Development," in *Advances in Chemical Engineering*, vol. 36, H. I. de Lasa and B. Serrano Rosales, Eds. Academic Press, 2009, pp. 111–143.
- [4] L. Lin, T. Hisatomi, S. Chen, T. Takata, and K. Domen, "Visible-Light-Driven Photocatalytic Water Splitting: Recent Progress and Challenges," *Trends in Chemistry*, vol. 2, no. 9, pp. 813–824, Sep. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trechm.2020.06.006>.
- [5] H. A. Maddah, "Numerical analysis for the oxidation of phenol with TiO₂ in wastewater photocatalytic reactors," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 3463–3469, Oct. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2304>
- [6] M. Mahshidnia and A. Jafarian, "Forecasting wastewater treatment results with an ANFIS intelligent system", *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 6, no. 5, pp. 1175–1181, Oct. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.745>
- [7] M. Nadareishvili, G. Mamniashvili, D. Jishiashvili, G. Abramishvili, C. Ramana, and J. Ramsden, "Investigation of the visible light sensitive ZnO photocatalytic thin films," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 5524–5527, Apr. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3392>
- [8] D. Japaridze *et al.*, "Magnetic Properties and Photocatalytic Activity of the TiO₂ Micropowders and Nanopowders Coated by Ni Nanoclusters," *Journal of Superconductivity and Novel Magnetism*, vol. 32, no. 10, pp. 3211–3216, Oct. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10948-019-5088-2>.
- [9] M. Nadareishvili *et al.*, "Decoration of photocatalytic TiO₂ particles by cobalt clusters," *Nanotechnology Perceptions*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 336–347, Nov. 2020.
- [10] T. Gavasheli, G. Mamniashvili, M. Nadareishvili, and T. Zedginidze, "Electroless Technology for Production of Cobalt Magnetic and Photocatalytic Nanopowders and Nanowires," *TechConnect Briefs*, vol. 2019, pp. 42–45, Jun. 2019.
- [11] Q. Zhang, M. Xu, B. You, Q. Zhang, H. Yuan, and K. Ostrikov, "Oxygen Vacancy-Mediated ZnO Nanoparticle Photocatalyst for Degradation of Methylene Blue," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 8, no. 3, Mar. 2018, Art. no. 353, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app8030353>.
- [12] T. N. Khoperia, T. Zedginidze, K. Kvavadze, and M. Nadareishvili, "Development of competitive nanotechnologies for solution of challenges in photocatalysis, electronics and composites fabrication," *ECS Meeting Abstracts*, no. 2, 2007, Art. no. 107.
- [13] T. N. Khoperia, T. I. Zedginidze, and T. Gegechkori, "Magnetic and Catalytic Properties of Electroless Nickel, Ni-P and Ni-P-Re Thin Films," *ECS Transactions*, vol. 25, no. 24, Feb. 2010, Art. no. 97, <https://doi.org/10.1149/1.3316118>.
- [14] T. Khoperia, G. Mamniashvili, M. Nadareishvili, and T. Zedginidze, "Competitive Nanotechnology for Deposition of Films and Fabrication of Powder-Like Particles," *ECS Transactions*, vol. 35, no. 10, Oct. 2011, Art. no. 17, <https://doi.org/10.1149/1.3640401>.
- [15] G. I. Mamniashvili *et al.*, "Magnetometry and Hyperthermia Study of Magnetic Fluid Preparation UNIMAG," *World Journal of Condensed Matter Physics*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 6–12, Feb. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.4236/wjcmp.2014.41002>.
- [16] G. C. Papaefthymiou, "Nanoparticle magnetism," *Nano Today*, vol. 4, no. 5, pp. 438–447, Oct. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nantod.2009.08.006>.
- [17] M. Nadareishvili, T. Zedginidze, and E. Chikvaidze, "On the Possibility of Improving the Efficiency of Oxide Photocatalysts," in *IV International scientific and practical conference "Scientific progress: innovations, achievements and prospects*, Munich, Germany, 2023, pp. 138–141.

Persistent Voltage Control of a Wind Turbine-Driven Isolated Multiphase Induction Machine

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ABSTRACT

The growing concern about the energy crisis and environmental protection has caused a growing interest in wind power generation systems. Researchers and engineers urgently need to create new multiphase induction machines for the production of wind energy, since they are essential parts of wind turbines. This study offers control and stability analysis of a multiphase induction machine based on the entropy stability requirements for its linearized model. The generated model was used to assess the on-load properties of the multiphase induction machine and calculate its steady-state parameters under each operating circumstance. According to the analysis, the eigenvalues depend on the machine parameters, with the excitation capacitance and speed variation being the most important. Stabilization of the multiphase induction machine is the main focus of the singular values, which vary according to its variables. The simulated results include an examination of a multiphase induction machine steady state for voltage build-up at various types of load.

Keywords-multi-phase machine; efficiency curves; stability analysis; equivalent circuit; control strategies

I. INTRODUCTION

Research on power transmission has gone beyond three phases [1-2], and multiphase induction machines have become much more significant [3-4]. Multiphase machines are seen as an alternative to three-phase machines for applications that need a range of speeds. As the demand for wind turbines and sustainable mobility increases worldwide, multiphase machines have become one of the preferred options for power conversion systems. Research on multiphase machines is becoming more and more popular due to the development of power semiconductor devices and converter modulation techniques. The stator excitation in a multiphase machine produces improved magneto-motive force, resulting in lower space harmonics, lower torque ripples, and higher efficiency than in three-phase drives. Multiphase drives also offer many other exceptional advantages over traditional three-phase drives [5-6]. Additional phases, strong reliability standards, and higher power ratings provide the system with more room for advancement, making multiphase machines preferable to their three-phase counterparts. As a result, research on multiphase machines has been expanding [7-8]. High-phase machines provide greater operating flexibility and fault tolerance compared to their three-phase counterparts [9-10].

In this study, the multiphase machine under investigation used a single three-phase winding set excitation technique. At least three different loading topologies can be used. For example, a load could be fed by a six-phase transformer that interfaces with the load. Although de-rating of the load is rarely necessary when even two phases are lost, such a configuration produces an exceedingly fault-resilient loading architecture [11-12]. Energy is regularly extracted from many renewable energy sources, such as small hydro plants, wind turbines, etc., using six-phase induction generators, since they have several benefits, including ease of construction, low cost, toughness, high dependability, and low maintenance requirements [13-14]. Multiphase induction generators have many advantages over conventional three-phase systems. Systems with more than three phases have recently attracted a great deal of interest in variable-speed drive electric systems [15-16]. Multiphase machines are used in important applications that demand strong fault-tolerant capabilities, such as submarine propulsion, aircraft, and undoubtedly Electric Vehicles (EVs) [17-20].

The loss of one phase does not cause a breakdown of the spinning magnetic field in three-phase machines without a neutral-point connection. Three phases are the bare minimum that can be used to provide the required rotational field. A multiphase machine can still operate without stopping if one of

the phases is open-circuited [21-24]. Multiphase induction generators can easily increase the total amount of power while maintaining the prior per-phase power rating. However, compared to multiphase induction generators, research on multiphase induction motors has been more fruitful to date [25-28]. Due to their higher reliability, multiphase machines are beginning to be accepted as alternatives in high-power applications because of their potential to create fault-tolerant operating procedures. High-power applications also have the advantage of requiring half as much power per phase for any given output power, allowing the use of power semiconductors with lower ratings than three-phase systems [30-34].

This study focuses on the working modes of a multiphase induction machine, determining the static performance of the self-excited generator at no and under load and examining the influence of capacity and speed variation on the electrical quantities. All analytical and numerical simulation studies were validated by experimental tests using a prototype available in the laboratory.

II. MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF MPIM

Figure 1 shows the schematic architecture of a multiphase induction generator for its two different sets of three-phase stator windings and one rotor winding. There is an arbitrary angle that separates these two sets of three-phase stator windings from the stars.

Fig. 1. Configuration of a wind-based MPIM.

$$[A] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{R_s}{\sigma} \left(1 - \frac{l_s^2 L_a}{\sigma L_s^2}\right) & 0 & -\frac{R_s}{\sigma L_s} \left(l_{sm} + \frac{l_s L_a}{\sigma L_s}\right) & 0 & -\frac{R_s l_s L_a}{\sigma l_r L_s} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{R_s}{\sigma} \left(1 - \frac{l_s l_s L_a}{\sigma L_s^2}\right) & 0 & -\frac{R_s}{\sigma L_s} \left(l_{sm} + \frac{l_s L_a}{\sigma L_s}\right) & 0 & -\frac{R_{s1} l_{s2} L_a}{\sigma l_r L_{s2}} \\ \frac{R_s}{\sigma} \left(1 - \frac{l_s^2 L_a}{\sigma L_s^2}\right) & 0 & -\frac{R_s}{\sigma L_s} \left(l_{sm} + \frac{l_s L_a}{\sigma L_s}\right) & 0 & -\frac{R_{s2} l_s L_a}{\sigma l_r L_s} & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{R_s}{\sigma} \left(1 - \frac{l_s^2 L_a}{\sigma L_s^2}\right) & 0 & -\frac{R_s}{\sigma L_s} \left(l_{sm} + \frac{l_s L_a}{\sigma L_s}\right) & 0 & -\frac{R_s l_s L_a}{\sigma l_r L_s} \\ -\frac{R_r L_a l_s}{\sigma L_s l_r} & 0 & -\frac{R_r L_a l_s}{\sigma L_s l_r} & 0 & \frac{R_r}{l_r} \left(1 - \frac{L_a}{l_r}\right) & w_e \\ 0 & -\frac{R_r L_a l_s}{\sigma L_s l_r} & 0 & -\frac{R_r L_a l_s}{\sigma L_s l_r} & -w_e & \frac{R_r}{l_r} \left(1 - \frac{L_a}{l_r}\right) \end{bmatrix}$$

with $L_s = l_s + l_{sm}$ and $\sigma = L_s - \frac{l_{sm}^2}{L_s}$ (4)

The magnetizing flux values are given by:

Figure 2 shows the d - q model applied as the loading is applied.

Fig. 2. Park transformation of multi-phase induction generator.

The multi-stator winding induction machine model was developed as follows:

$$[X] = [\lambda_{ds1} \lambda_{qs1} \lambda_{ds2} \lambda_{qs2} \lambda_{dr} \lambda_{qr}]^t \quad (1)$$

$$[V] = [V_{ds1} \ V_{qs1} \ V_{ds2} \ V_{qs2} \ 0 \ 0]^t \quad (2)$$

$$[A] = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{cases} \lambda_{dm} = L_a \left(\lambda_{ds1} \frac{l_s}{\sigma L_s} + \lambda_{ds2} \frac{l_s}{\sigma L_s} + \lambda_{dr} \frac{1}{l_r} \right) \\ \lambda_{qm} = L_a \left(\lambda_{qs1} \frac{l_s}{\sigma L_s} + \lambda_{qs2} \frac{l_s}{\sigma L_s} + \lambda_{qr} \frac{1}{l_r} \right) \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where:

$$L_a = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{L_m} + \frac{2L_s}{\sigma L_s} + \frac{1}{l_r}} \quad (6)$$

Using the state variables, the following set of equations can be defined:

$$\begin{cases} i_{ds1} = \frac{1}{\sigma} \left(1 - \frac{l_s^2 L_a}{\sigma L_s^2}\right) \lambda_{ds1} - \frac{1}{\sigma L_s} \left(l_{sm} + \frac{l_s l_a}{\sigma L_s}\right) \lambda_{ds2} - \left(\frac{l_s l_a}{\sigma l_r L_s}\right) \lambda_{dr} \\ i_{qs1} = \frac{1}{\sigma} \left(1 - \frac{l_s^2 L_a}{\sigma L_s^2}\right) \lambda_{qs1} - \frac{1}{\sigma L_s} \left(l_{sm} + \frac{l_s l_a}{\sigma L_s}\right) \lambda_{qs2} - \left(\frac{l_s l_a}{\sigma l_r L_s}\right) \lambda_{qr} \\ i_{ds2} = \frac{1}{\sigma} \left(1 - \frac{l_s^2 L_a}{\sigma L_s^2}\right) \lambda_{ds2} - \frac{1}{\sigma L_s} \left(l_{sm} + \frac{l_s l_a}{\sigma L_s}\right) \lambda_{ds1} - \left(\frac{l_s l_a}{\sigma l_r L_s}\right) \lambda_{dr} \\ i_{qs2} = \frac{1}{\sigma} \left(1 - \frac{l_s^2 L_a}{\sigma L_s^2}\right) \lambda_{qs2} - \frac{1}{\sigma L_s} \left(l_{sm} + \frac{l_s l_a}{\sigma L_s}\right) \lambda_{qs1} - \left(\frac{l_s l_a}{\sigma l_r L_s}\right) \lambda_{qr} \\ i_{dr} = -\left(\frac{L_a l_s}{\sigma L_s l_r}\right) \lambda_{ds1} - \left(\frac{L_a l_s}{\sigma L_s l_r}\right) \lambda_{ds2} + \frac{1}{l_r} \left(1 - \frac{L_a}{l_r}\right) \lambda_{dr} \\ i_{qr} = -\left(\frac{L_a l_s}{\sigma L_s l_r}\right) \lambda_{qs1} - \left(\frac{L_a l_s}{\sigma L_s l_r}\right) \lambda_{qs2} + \frac{1}{l_r} \left(1 - \frac{L_a}{l_r}\right) \lambda_{qr} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

III. SIMULATION AND PERFORMANCE RESULTS

To examine how the multiphase induction machine performs, both sets of the three-phase windings of the stator were connected to a variety of excitation capacitors. Figure 3 shows the diagrammatic representation of a multiphase induction machine operating in shunt mode. The test device was subjected to several conditions, including no load and loads with varying speeds and excitation capacitor values. Table I lists the generator parameters that were established by the laboratory machines' no-load and locked-rotor tests.

TABLE I. PARAMETERS OF THE GENERATOR

Sn	0.5 KW
VLL	220 V
ns	1500 rpm
I	0.75 A
f	50 Hz
Rs	28.59 Ω
Rr	14.38 Ω
Xr	19.81 Ω
Xsm	20.1 Ω
Xs	19.81 Ω

Two sets of specifically designed three-phase windings were used to rewind the stator of each machine (two stars).

A. Control Strategy of Unloaded MPIM

As no voltage is necessary for autonomous operation, the multiphase induction machine's rated voltage and current parameters listed on the equipment rating plate were used to calculate power limits, as shown in Figure 3. Voltage is sensitive to capacitance fluctuation for a specific rotational speed value. The generator starts from a minimum capacity $C_{min} = 6.47 \mu F$ which corresponds to a voltage $V_{min} = 95V$.

The machine could burn if the excitation capacity is increased because it will increase the voltage applied to the stator. Two capacity limit values were found for a given speed, one for the generator beginning and the other for the nominal voltage: $C \in [6.47, 8.19] \mu F$. As a result, the vacuum generator's stable operating range is limited at high rotation rates. The device starts at its rated speed $W_{emin} = 279.4 \text{ rad/s}$, which corresponds to a voltage $V = 8323 \text{ V}$, for a certain capacity. For a W_{emax} rated speed of 314.2 rad/s , the

machine's rated voltage $V = 220 \text{ V}$ is obtained as shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 3. Variation of voltage with capacitance.

Fig. 4. Stator voltage against speed for constant capacity $C = 8.19 \mu F$.

When the speed exceeds the voltage, there is a high risk of overheating (W_{emax}) and the occurrence of damage to the machine's insulation. As a result, the speed value should be selected with care. To define the stable operating zone of the generator for self-excited induction, it is helpful to know the speed at which extreme values change, and therefore the reliable operating range of the generator is defined for a particular capacity by $\omega_{min} < \omega_e < \omega_{e \max}$. As the excitation power rises, the stable operating range of the vacuum generator; therefore, performance at large excitation capacities is of special relevance.

B. Stability Analysis for Loaded Six-Phase Induction Generator

It can be shown that the machine's terminal voltage is more critical than the vacuum. Figure 5 shows that as the load is reduced, the voltage decreases, the current increases to its peak, and then both the voltage and the current drop to zero. Z_{max} exceeds the nominal operating conditions of the generator. As a result, Z_{min} has a minimum value below which the machine's excitement is gone. By doing this, a load range is created that guarantees that the generator will run nonstop. The selection of the load impedance must meet the following criteria:

$$Z_{min} \leq Z_{ch} \leq Z_{max} \quad (8)$$

Excitation capacity, drive speed, and load impedance affect the terminal voltage of the autonomous asynchronous generator. Figure 6 shows the performance of the machine.

Fig. 5. Stable operating zone under load for $C = 8.65 \mu\text{F}$ and $w_e = 314.2 \text{ rad/s}$.

Fig. 6. Stator voltage against load current for various speeds ($\omega_{ei} = 300 \text{ rad/s}$, $\omega_{ef} = 316 \text{ rad/s}$, $\Delta w_e = 2 \text{ rad/s}$, $C = 9.5 \mu\text{F}$).

TABLE II. EFFECT OF THE ROTATIONAL SPEED ON THE CRITICAL LOAD IMPEDANCE VALUES.

Speed	316 rad/s	314 rad/s	312 rad/s
Zmin	579.29Ω	592.14Ω	605.83Ω
Zmax	1626Ω	1826Ω	2097.23Ω

Table II shows that as the fixed rotational speed capacity increases, the voltage changes as a function of the load current, and the extreme values of the load impedance decrease. This reduces the variation of the load range and, as a result, the stable working range of the generator load. This creates a load range that ensures that the generator will run continuously. Impedance under maximum load decreases as the current flows are increased for a certain rotational speed. The generator's performance under load is significantly influenced by its capacitance and speed.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Technology for multiphase machines has advanced significantly in the last ten years. This study offered a thorough analysis of a multiphase induction generator that has been successfully modeled in a fixed reference frame utilizing a different modeling strategy. The selection of the ideal excitation capacitance and some other factors, relevant to the implementation of the high-phase multiphase induction generator, were addressed in depth. The ideal excitation

capacitance for the machine under investigation was determined by experimental research. The simulation findings show that the generator has excellent voltage control because of series compensation. The generating system is capable of producing output voltage at a constant frequency. Moreover, the electricity from the energy storage element can be switched to the AC side in an emergency.

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REFERENCES

- [1] H. Mellah, S. Arslan, H. Sahraoui, K. E. Hemsas, and S. Kamel, "The Effect of Stator Inter-Turn Short-Circuit Fault on DFIG Performance Using FEM," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 8688–8693, Jun. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4923>.
- [2] A. Guediri, "Study and Order of a Medium Power Wind Turbine Conversion Chain Connected to Medium Voltage Grid," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 7279–7282, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4169>.
- [3] H. H. Bui, "Control Design for the Ward-Leonard System in Wind Turbines," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 9968–9972, Feb. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5425>.
- [4] M. A. Khelifi and M. B. Slimene, "Efficiency of a Six-Phase Induction Generator Employing a Static Excitation Controller to Generate AC Power for Wind Energy," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 28791–28799, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3260775>.
- [5] M. Ben Slimene and M. A. Khelifi, "Investigation on the Effects of Magnetic Saturation in Six-Phase Induction Machines with and without Cross Saturation of the Main Flux Path," *Energies*, vol. 15, no. 24, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 9412, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15249412>.
- [6] H. P. Nabi, P. Dadashi, and A. Shoulaie, "A novel structure for vector control of a symmetrical six-phase induction machine with three current sensors," in *2011 10th International Conference on Environment and Electrical Engineering*, Rome, Italy, Feb. 2011, pp. 1–5, <https://doi.org/10.1109/EEEIC.2011.5874735>.
- [7] M. A. Khelifi, "Explaining the d-q Magnetic Couplings Theoretically in Saturated Smooth Air-Gap AC Machines," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 3739–3743, Feb. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2327>.
- [8] I. Sami, S. Ullah, Z. Ali, N. Ullah, and J.-S. Ro, "A Super Twisting Fractional Order Terminal Sliding Mode Control for DFIG-Based Wind Energy Conversion System," *Energies*, vol. 13, no. 9, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 2158, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13092158>.
- [9] M. M. Alhato, M. N. Ibrahim, H. Rezk, and S. Bouallègue, "An Enhanced DC-Link Voltage Response for Wind-Driven Doubly Fed Induction Generator Using Adaptive Fuzzy Extended State Observer and Sliding Mode Control," *Mathematics*, vol. 9, no. 9, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 963, <https://doi.org/10.3390/math9090963>.
- [10] H. Benbouhenni, Z. Boudjema, and A. Belaidi, "DPC Based on ANFIS Super-Twisting Sliding Mode Algorithm of a Doubly-Fed Induction Generator for Wind Energy System," *Journal Européen des Systèmes Automatisés*, vol. 53, no. 1, pp. 69–80, Feb. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.18280/jesa.530109>.
- [11] B. Farid, B. Tarek, and B. Sebti, "Fuzzy super twisting algorithm dual direct torque control of doubly fed induction machine," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 11, no. 5, Oct. 2021, Art. no. 3782, <https://doi.org/10.11591/ijece.v11i5.pp3782-3790>.
- [12] N. Ullah, I. Sami, Md. S. Chowdhury, K. Techato, and H. I. Alkhamash, "Artificial Intelligence Integrated Fractional Order Control of Doubly Fed Induction Generator-Based Wind Energy

- System," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 5734–5748, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3048420>.
- [13] A. Guediri and S. Touil, "Modeling and Comparison of Fuzzy-PI and Genetic Control Algorithms for Active and Reactive Power Flow between the Stator (DFIG) and the Grid," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 8640–8645, Jun. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4905>.
- [14] F. Bu, Y. Hu, W. Huang, S. Zhuang, and K. Shi, "Wide-Speed-Range-Operation Dual Stator-Winding Induction Generator DC Generating System for Wind Power Applications," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 30, no. 2, pp. 561–573, Oct. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPEL.2014.2308222>.
- [15] M. B. Slimene and M. A. Khelifi, "Performance Limits of Three-Phase Self-Excited Induction Generator (SEIG) as a Stand Alone DER," *Journal of Electrical Engineering & Technology*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 145–150, Jan. 2017.
- [16] M. A. Khelifi and H. Rehaoulia, "General modeling of saturated AC machines for industrial drives," *COMPEL: The International Journal for Computation and Mathematics in Electrical and Electronic Engineering*, vol. 35, no. 1, pp. 44–63, Jan. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1108/COMPEL-12-2014-0346>.
- [17] M. A. Taghikhani and A. D. Farahani, "A Reactive Power Based Reference Model for Adaptive Control Strategy in a SEIG," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 2477–2484, Feb. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1701>.
- [18] M. B. Slimene, M. A. Khelifi, M. B. Fredj, and H. Rehaoulia, "Modeling of a Dual Stator Induction Generator with and Without Cross Magnetic Saturation," *Journal of Magnetism*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 284–289, Sep. 2015.
- [19] M. Ben Slimene, M. A. Khelifi, M. Ben Fredj, and H. Rehaoulia, "Analysis of Saturated Self-Excited Dual Stator Induction Generator for Wind Energy Generation," *Journal of Circuits, Systems and Computers*, vol. 24, no. 09, Art. no. 1550129, Oct. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0218126615501297>.
- [20] M. A. Khelifi and B. M. Alshammari, "Steady State Analysis of an Isolated Self-Excited Dual Three-Phase Induction Generator for Renewable Energy," *International Journal of Modern Nonlinear Theory and Application*, vol. 03, no. 05, Nov. 2014, Art. no. 191, <https://doi.org/10.4236/ijmnta.2014.35021>.
- [21] B. S. Marwa, A. K. Mohamed, B. F. Mouldi, and R. Habib, "Effect of the stator mutual leakage reactance of dual stator induction generator," *International Journal of Electrical Energy*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 1810–1818, 2014.
- [22] M. B. Slimene, M. A. Khelifi, M. Benfredj, and H. Rehaoulia, "The Process of Self Excitation in Dual Three-Phase Induction Generator," *International Review of Electrical Engineering*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 1738–1743, Dec. 2013.
- [23] M. A. Khelifi, M. Ben Slimene, M. Ben Fredj, and H. Rhaoulia, "Performance evaluation of self-excited DSIG as a stand-alone distributed energy resources," *Electrical Engineering*, vol. 98, no. 2, pp. 159–167, Jun. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00202-015-0349-y>.
- [24] M. Slunjski, O. Dordevic, M. Jones, and E. Levi, "Symmetrical/Asymmetrical Winding Reconfiguration in Multiphase Machines," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 12835–12844, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2965652>.
- [25] J. Paredes, B. Prieto, M. Satrustegui, I. Elósegui, and P. González, "Improving the Performance of a 1-MW Induction Machine by Optimally Shifting From a Three-Phase to a Six-Phase Machine Design by Rearranging the Coil Connections," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 68, no. 2, pp. 1035–1045, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIE.2020.2969099>.
- [26] Y. Wang, J. Yang, R. Deng, and G. Yang, "Parameters estimation for multiphase induction machine with concentrated windings through finite element method," *IET Electric Power Applications*, vol. 14, no. 10, pp. 1807–1817, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1049/iet-epa.2019.0869>.
- [27] T. S. de Souza, R. R. Bastos, and B. J. Cardoso Filho, "Synchronous-Frame Modeling and dq Current Control of an Unbalanced Nine-Phase Induction Motor Due to Open Phases," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 56, no. 2, pp. 2097–2106, Mar. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIA.2020.2965493>.
- [28] P. Drozdowski and D. Cholewa, "Voltage Control of Multiphase Cage Induction Generators at a Speed Varying over a Wide Range," *Energies*, vol. 14, no. 21, Art. no. 7080, Jan. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14217080>.
- [29] M. F. Khan and M. R. Khan, "Modeling and Analysis of a Six-Phase Self Excited Induction Generator Feeding Induction Motors," *IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion*, vol. 36, no. 2, pp. 746–754, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TEC.2020.3013784>.
- [30] A. Gonzalez-Prieto, I. González-Prieto, M. J. Duran, and J. J. Aciego, "Dynamic Response in Multiphase Electric Drives: Control Performance and Influencing Factors," *Machines*, vol. 10, no. 10, Oct. 2022, Art. no. 866, <https://doi.org/10.3390/machines10100866>.
- [31] M. R. Arahali, M. G. Satué, F. Barrero, and C. Martín, "Online Adaptive Set of Virtual Voltage Vectors for Stator Current Regulation of a Six-Phase Induction Machine Using Finite State Model Predictive Controllers," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 13, no. 7, Jan. 2023, Art. no. 4113, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13074113>.
- [32] L. Li, W. Zhou, X. Bi, X. Sun, and X. Shi, "Second-Order Model-Based Predictive Control of Dual Three-Phase PMSM Based on Current Loop Operation Optimization," *Actuators*, vol. 11, no. 9, Sep. 2022, Art. no. 251, <https://doi.org/10.3390/act11090251>.
- [33] W. Taha, P. Azer, A. D. Callegaro, and A. Emadi, "Multiphase Traction Inverters: State-of-the-Art Review and Future Trends," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 4580–4599, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3141542>.
- [34] K. B. Tawfiq, M. N. Ibrahim, E. E. EL-Kholy, and P. Sergeant, "Performance Analysis of a Rewound Multiphase Synchronous Reluctance Machine," *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 297–309, Oct. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1109/JESTPE.2021.3106591>.

Effective Feature Prediction Models for Student Performance

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ABSTRACT

The ability to accurately predict how students will perform has a significant impact on the teaching and learning process, as it can inform the instructor to devote extra attention to a particular student or group of students, which in turn prevents those students from failing a certain course. When it comes to educational data mining, the accuracy and explainability of predictions are of equal importance. Accuracy refers to the degree to which the predicted value was accurate, and explainability refers to the degree to which the predicted value could be understood. This study used machine learning to predict the features that best contribute to the performance of a student, using a dataset collected from a public university in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia. Experimental analysis was carried out with Black-Box (BB) and White-Box (WB)

machine-learning classification models. In BB classification models, a decision (or class) is often predicted with limited explainability on why this decision was made, while in WB classification models decisions made are fully interpretable to the stakeholders. The results showed that these BB models performed similarly in terms of accuracy and recall whether the classifiers attempted to predict an A or an F grade. When comparing the classifiers' accuracy in making predictions on B grade, the Support Vector Machine (SVM) was found to be superior to Naïve Bayes (NB). However, the recall results were quite similar except for the K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN) classifier. When predicting grades C and D, RF had the best accuracy and NB the worst. RF had the best recall when predicting a C grade, while NB had the lowest. When predicting a D grade, SVM had the best recall performance, while NB had the lowest.

Keywords-student performance; artificial neural networks; support vector machine; Naïve Bayes; k-nearest neighbor

I. INTRODUCTION

Machine Learning (ML) models enable machines to make predictions. In general, ML models are categorized into supervised, unsupervised, and reinforcement models. Many studies have demonstrated how to successfully involve ML models to solve problems involving predictions [1-19]. The learning processes are different from category to category. Models can learn by providing the input data and its corresponding output (supervised learning), providing only input data (unsupervised learning), or providing only rewards (reinforcement learning). In many cases, ML models contain hundreds of nodes that are connected to solve a given problem. It is difficult for humans to understand the intuition behind the predictions made. For this, an ANN is often denoted as a Black-Box (BB) model, where it is difficult for domain experts to "see" inside it and "understand" why it is making certain decisions. This lack of interpretability of the model and the explainability of the decision causes a trust issue. Deep learning is another common example of BB models, as it is difficult for a human to understand the millions or billions of calculations made by such algorithms. For that, some domains, such as healthcare and the military, enforce regulations and constraints when using ML to make important decisions.

According to the Statement on Algorithmic Transparency and Accountability [20], providing explanations of the algorithm's decision-making process is becoming mandatory. This is because some algorithms can lead to harmful bias, which can have a legal or financial impact or incorrect predictions. Fortunately, this encouraged the development of methods that are used to explain BB models. This growing area of research is often known as explainable AI (XAI), which aims to develop methods that explain AI systems to their stakeholders [17]. This is important when these systems are too complex or ambiguous and encompasses the underlying causes of the system's methods or procedures to provide information that helps various stakeholders to better understand these systems. In XAI, explainable methods are classified into global or local, where global methods explain the prediction of all instances and local methods explain the prediction for a particular instance or group of instances [15]. On the other hand, some models are inherently interpretable because there is no need for additional steps to explain their behavior. This category of models is often denoted as White-Box (WB) models [19]. Such models include Decision Trees (DT), Rule-Based (RB) systems, Contrast Patterns (CP), and Fuzzy Patterns (FP). Often, these WB models provide a trade-off between accuracy and explainability, meaning that training BB

models will often provide better accuracy than WB. Due to this assumption, researchers seek to use BB models by adding a layer of explainability on top of them. However, in [21], it was stated that state-of-the-art WB models can achieve prediction performance comparable to BB models, and their use is encouraged instead of explaining BB models. This study aimed to train state-of-the-art WB models in the educational data mining domain and systematically compare their performance against BB models. Educational Data Mining (EDM) aims to develop methods that study and explore educational data that could be from face-to-face education, e-learning and Learning Management Systems (LMSs) or Intelligent Tutoring Systems (ITSs), and Adaptive Educational Hypermedia Systems (AEHSs) [17]. After analyzing educational data, EDM tries to evaluate the educational systems to improve the learning processes and better understand learners and learning.

In [1], four data mining techniques, ANN, DT, SVM, and Naïve Bayes (NB), were used on a dataset from Princess Norah University with a total of 4,078 students who took the General Aptitude Test (GAT) and the Scholastic Achievement Admission Test (SAAT). The four classifiers were compared for their accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score, showing that ANN was the best in terms of accuracy (79%) and precision (81%), while DT was the best in terms of recall (80%) and F1-score (81%) and the NB classifier exhibited the worst performance. In [4], regression algorithms were used on a dataset of 85 students and 3 student feature classes: personal features, educational features, and behavioral features. In [3], a recommendation system used RF, DT, and Linear Regression (LR) to maintain the best behavior for the proposed system. In [11], exploratory factor analysis, multiple linear regressions, cluster analysis, and correlations were used to predict student academic performance. In [8], a nonlinear predictive model was proposed that can be explained using the SHAP game-theory-based framework. In [6], a warning system was proposed using Multi-View Genetic Programming (MVGP). In [10], a prediction model was developed that used Genetic Programming-Interpretable Classification Rule Mining (GP-ICRM) that was optimal and interpretable. In [12], a model was proposed that used a rule-based genetic programming algorithm for prediction, achieving good performance with 89% precision, 86.7% recall, 87.5 F1-score, and 89.9% ROC-score. In [2], several WB and BB models were used. This study aimed to use CORELS, which is an interpretable model, and compare its performance with several WB and BB models to test the claim that SOTA interpretable models can achieve prediction performance comparable to BB [21].

II. PRELIMINARIES

A. Problem Definition

This study aims to predict the success or failure of a student in a specific course. Let $x(j)$ be a $1 \times n$ vector of student j grades at selected courses, where n is the number of selected courses, m is the number of students in the dataset, and $j = (1, \dots, m)$. When packing $x(j)$ row by row, an $m \times n$ matrix X of student-course grades is obtained. Let X_t denote student-course grades at time $\leq t$. Let $y(t+1)$ denote the student-course grade for a selected course at time $\geq t$, such that $y(t+1) \in \{0, 1\}$, where 0 indicates failing a course and 1 indicates passing it. The objective is to predict a student's performance in a new course, given his/her performance in previous courses, in the form of a function f that maps input X_t to output $y(t+1)$ as:

$$y(t + 1) = f(X_t) \tag{1}$$

Predicting students' passing or failing a course is a binary classification problem since $y(t+1)$ can be 0 or 1. The input X_t , that is, student grades, can be numerical or categorical, where numerical grades range from 0 to 100, and categorical grades can either be binary (0 or 1) to indicate failing or passing a course, or discretized letter grades (A+, A, B+, B, C+, ...). This study tested the proposed model on selected courses from the dataset.

B. Data Description and Preprocessing

This study used a dataset collected from a public university located in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia, which contained student enrollment records, each having student ID, course ID, and the grade obtained. The dataset had a total of 250 students and 180 courses collected from 2015 to 2019. At first, the unnecessary features were removed from the dataset. Then, the maximum, minimum, mean, median, and standard deviation of the grades were calculated for each student, course, and teacher, as shown in Table II. The dataset was discretized, as shown in Table III, by converting the continuous data into categorical. Performance was evaluated in terms of accuracy, recall,

precision, complexity matrix, and speed. Accuracy is the ratio of correct predictions to the total number of input samples (3), while the complexity metric measures the ratio between the number of classes and the number of rules (4) [14]. Recall and precision, as shown in (1) and (2), are similar to accuracy but are often used on unbalanced data. Lastly, the speed of the model measures how fast the model can be trained and tested.

$$Recall = \frac{True\ Positives}{True\ Positives + False\ Negatives} \tag{1}$$

$$Precision = \frac{True\ Positives}{True\ Positives + False\ Positives} \tag{2}$$

$$Accuracy = \frac{Number\ of\ Correct\ Predictions}{Total\ Number\ of\ Predictions} \tag{3}$$

$$Complexity = \frac{l}{\sum_{i=1}^r k_r} \tag{4}$$

where l is the number of classes (2 in this case), r is the number of rules, and k is the number of features used in the i -th rule [14].

TABLE I. SYMBOL NOTATIONS

Notation	Description
S	Student
C	Course
T	Teacher
n	Number of courses
m	Number of Students

Fig. 1. Grade distribution.

TABLE II. DATASET STATISTICS ON THE GRADE OF EACH STUDENT, COURSE, AND TEACHER.

S avg	T avg	C avg	S med	T med	C med	S std	T std	C std	S min	T min	C min	S max	T max	C max
60.0	65.4	66.0	60.0	68.0	70.0	0.0	20.6	18.5	60.0	3.0	3.0	60.0	97.0	97.0
70.0	68.3	67.9	70.0	67.5	65.0	0.0	6.5	6.2	70.0	60.0	60.0	70.0	75.0	75.0
72.7	73.5	78.5	75.0	80.0	84.0	4.8	19.6	18.5	66.0	11.0	11.0	77.0	96.0	96.0
72.7	69.4	73.4	75.0	71.0	73.0	4.8	13.2	11.8	66.0	29.0	33.0	77.0	92.0	100.0
72.7	74.1	72.4	75.0	75.0	74.0	4.8	13.1	15.2	66.0	38.0	13.0	77.0	96.0	99.0

TABLE III. DATASET AFTER DISCRETIZATION

S avg	T avg	C avg	S med	T med	C med	S std	T std	C std	S min	T min	C min	S max	T max	C max
(59, 69]	(59, 69]	(59, 69]	(59, 69]	(59, 69]	(69, 79]	(-0.001, 2.944]	(16.214, 23.629]	(15.153, 18.543]	(59, 69]	(0, 59]	(0, 59]	(59, 69]	(89, 100]	(89, 100]
(69, 79]	(59, 69]	(59, 69]	(69, 79]	(59, 69]	(59, 69]	(-0.001, 2.944]	(4.443, 11.306]	(5.782, 11.819]	(69, 79]	(59, 69]	(59, 69]	(69, 79]	(69, 79]	(69, 79]
(69, 79]	(69, 79]	(69, 79]	(69, 79]	(79, 89]	(79, 89]	(2.944, 6.128]	(16.214, 23.629]	(15.153, 18.543]	(59, 69]	(0, 59]	(0, 59]	(69, 79]	(89, 100]	(89, 100]
(69, 79]	(69, 79]	(69, 79]	(69, 79]	(69, 79]	(69, 79]	(2.944, 6.128]	(11.306, 14.214]	(5.782, 11.819]	(59, 69]	(0, 59]	(0, 59]	(69, 79]	(89, 100]	(89, 100]
(69, 79]	(69, 79]	(69, 79]	(69, 79]	(69, 79]	(69, 79]	(2.944, 6.128]	(11.306, 14.214]	(11.819, 15.153]	(59, 69]	(0, 59]	(0, 59]	(69, 79]	(89, 100]	(89, 100]

TABLE IV. DATASET IN BINARY FORMAT

SAVG (0, 59]	SAVG (59, 69]	SAVG (69, 79]	SAVG (79, 89]	SAVG (89, 100]	T AVG (0, 59]	T AVG (59, 69]	...	T MAX (79, 89]	T MAX (89, 100]	C MAX (0, 59]	C MAX (59, 69]	C MAX (69, 79]	C MAX (79, 89]	C MAX (89, 100]
0	1	0	0	0	0	1	...	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
0	0	1	0	0	0	1	...	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
0	0	1	0	0	0	0	...	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
0	0	1	0	0	0	0	...	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
0	0	1	0	0	0	0	...	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
...
0	0	0	1	0	0	0	...	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
0	1	0	0	0	0	1	...	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
0	0	1	0	0	0	0	...	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
0	0	1	0	0	0	0	...	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
0	0	1	0	0	0	0	...	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
0	0	1	0	0	0	0	...	0	1	0	0	0	0	1

TABLE V. DATASET AFTER OVERSAMPLING

SAVG (0, 59]	SAVG (59, 69]	SAVG (69, 79]	SAVG (79, 89]	SAVG (89, 100]	T AVG (0, 59]	T AVG (59, 69]	...	T MAX (79, 89]	T MAX (89, 100]	C MAX (0, 59]	C MAX (59, 69]	C MAX (69, 79]	C MAX (79, 89]	C MAX (89,100]
0	1	0	0	0	0	1	...	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
0	0	1	0	0	0	1	...	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
0	0	1	0	0	0	0	...	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
0	0	1	0	0	0	0	...	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
0	0	1	0	0	0	0	...	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
...
0	1	0	0	0	0	1	...	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
1	0	0	0	0	0	1	...	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	...	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
1	0	0	0	0	0	1	...	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	...	0	1	0	0	0	0	1

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Framework Description

Figure 2 illustrates the framework. At first, the dataset was cleaned by removing unnecessary features and replacing all null values with zeros. Then, discretization was performed on the preprocessed dataset. After that, oversampling was used to equally split the dataset by every fold and obtain reasonable results from the unbalanced dataset. For every grade y, there is model training and testing, using the five-fold cross-validation technique. After cross-validation is performed, the average of every evaluation matrix is provided.

Fig. 2. Methodology framework.

B. Evaluation Metric

The 5-fold cross-validation was used to evaluate the model, where the dataset was split into five parts, and training and

testing were performed five times. For each of the five iterations, one dataset part was used for testing and the others were used for training. Evaluation metrics were calculated in the testing set in each iteration $i = 1 \dots kr$, where l is the number of classes (2 in this case), r is the number of rules, and k is the number of features used in the i -th rule [14].

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Experimental Settings

Jupyter Notebook was used as the development environment for Python3, along with Scikit-learn and Pandas for data analysis, Matplotlib for visualizations, and imodels for testing and evaluating the interpretable models. The tests were run on a MacBook Air laptop with a 1.1GHz quad-core Intel Core i5 CPU and 8 GB RAM.

B. Results

There are two types of ML models, WB and BB. WB models tend to be highly interpretable, meaning that it is easy for humans to understand the results provided, whereas BB models are not. The strength of WB models relies on finding biased results and preventing them from happening. This study selected CORELS as the main model, which is a state-of-the-art rule-based model that attempts to learn an optimal set of rules in each problem, and its performance was compared with several other WB and BB models. Standard Deviation (SD) measures the spread of the scores by the mean [22]. The results in Tables VI-XII have a very low SD after all the five folds, indicating good performance. As the dataset was unbalanced, the accuracy was 100% or close to it when predicting grades A and F for the CORELS, GreedyTree, C4.5, Bayesian Rule List (BRL), and Boosted Rules models without using the

oversampling technique. In contrast, the Slipper model was not as good as the other models at predicting grade A. The accuracy in predicting grades B, C, and D is reasonably acceptable for all models.

Table VIII shows that when the model predicted grade A, GreedyTree and C4.5 classifiers outperformed CORELS by 0.02 and 0.03, respectively, in accuracy, while CORELS outperformed the Slipper classifier by 0.02 in accuracy and had the same accuracy with Bayesian and Boosted classifiers. The recall results were very close to each other. When the model predicted grades B, C, and D, the accuracy results of the GreedyTree, C4.5, Bayesian, and Boosted classifiers outperformed CORELS, while the Slipper classifier underperformed. In recall, the CORELS, Greedy Tree, C4.5, Bayesian, and Boosted classifiers had similar results, while the Slipper classifier had the lowest recall in predicting grade B. The recall of CORELS in predicting grade C was lower than the GreedyTree, C4.5, Bayesian, and Boosted classifier, but higher than the Slipper classifier. When predicting grade D, CORELS outperformed GreedyTree, C4.5, Slipper, and Boosted classifiers but underperformed the Bayesian classifier. For predicting grade F, the accuracy and recall of all WB classifiers were similar [23].

Tables VII and VIII show that when using oversampling, accuracy did not change dramatically, but recall improved. When predicting grade B with CORELS, the recall was 0.64 without and 0.96 with oversampling, which means that oversampling improved the model's testing performance. Table

IX shows that CORELS took less training time than the C4.5, Bayesian, and Slipper classifiers. In addition, CORELS took more time to train than GreedyTree and Boosted classifiers, but had the least testing time among the rest WB classifiers. Table XI shows that the accuracy and recall results of these BB models were very similar when the classifiers predicted grades A and F. When the classifiers predicted grade B, SVM had the best accuracy results, while NB had the worst. On the other hand, the recall results are very close to each other except for the KNN classifier [24]. When the classifiers predicted grades C and D, RF had the best accuracy, and NB had the worst. When predicting grade C, RF had the best recall results, while NB had the worst. When predicting grade D, SVM had the best recall result and NB had the worst. Table XII shows that RF took the longest training time, while KNN took the shortest [25]. In addition, it is observed that RF took the longest testing time, while GB took the shortest. Moreover, when not using oversampling, Tables X and XI show that accuracy and recall were improved. When predicting grades A and F, WB and BB models had similar high accuracies. Moreover, WB models, except the Slipper classifier, had better accuracy than NB, SVM, and KNN when predicting grades B, C, and D. On the other hand, RF and GB models had similar accuracy as the WB models, except Slipper. Tables IX and XII show that C4.5, BRL, and Slipper models took longer time to process than BB models [26]. On the other hand, CORELS, BR, and GT took a similar time as the BB models. It can be stated that CORELS can provide high accuracy with minimal time.

TABLE VI. WB RESULTS

Classifier	Grade A			Grade B			Grade C			Grade D			Grade F		
	Acc.	Prec.	Rec.												
CORELS	1.0 (±0.00)	1.0 (±0.00)	1.0 (±0.00)	0.87 (±0.03)	0.75 (±0.07)	0.64 (±0.07)	0.80 (±0.02)	0.81 (±0.05)	0.42 (±0.03)	0.8 (±0.04)	0.76 (±0.05)	0.60 (±0.09)	0.95 (±0.01)	0.51 (±0.27)	0.49 (±0.00)
Greedy Tree	1.0 (±0.00)	1.0 (±0.00)	1.0 (±0.00)	0.87 (±0.04)	0.71 (±0.07)	0.67 (±0.05)	0.80 (±0.02)	0.65 (±0.09)	0.61 (±0.05)	0.78 (±0.05)	0.68 (±0.06)	0.65 (±0.07)	0.93 (±0.01)	0.56 (±0.15)	0.47 (±0.18)
C4.5 Tree	1.0 (±0.00)	1.0 (±0.00)	1.0 (±0.00)	0.87 (±0.04)	0.72 (±0.08)	0.65 (±0.14)	0.79 (±0.02)	0.66 (±0.09)	0.58 (±0.08)	0.79 (±0.05)	0.67 (±0.06)	0.67 (±0.06)	0.94 (±0.02)	0.52 (±0.17)	0.47 (±0.18)
BRL	0.89 (±0.02)	0.47 (±0.06)	1.0 (±0.00)	0.77 (±0.03)	0.49 (±0.02)	1.0 (±0.00)	0.69 (±0.04)	0.48 (±0.03)	0.99 (±0.02)	0.74 (±0.07)	0.55 (±0.06)	0.99 (±0.01)	0.94 (±0.00)	0.51 (±0.10)	1.0 (±0.00)
Boosted Rules	0.89 (±0.02)	0.47 (±0.06)	1.0 (±0.00)	0.83 (±0.03)	0.90 (±0.13)	0.29 (±0.09)	0.79 (±0.02)	0.85 (±0.13)	0.37 (±0.15)	0.83 (±0.02)	0.78 (±0.04)	0.64 (±0.08)	0.94 (±0.01)	0.53 (±0.09)	0.96 (±0.01)
Slipper	0.79 (±0.22)	0.68 (±0.30)	0.37 (±0.22)	0.83 (±0.04)	0.81 (±0.17)	0.36 (±0.12)	0.73 (±0.11)	0.82 (±0.18)	0.30 (±0.15)	0.80 (±0.03)	0.8 (±0.10)	0.44 (±0.14)	0.94 (±0.02)	0.53 (±0.24)	0.49 (±0.29)

TABLE VII. WB RESULTS WITHOUT OVERSAMPLING

Classifier	Grade A			Grade B			Grade C			Grade D			Grade F		
	Acc.	Prec.	Rec.												
CORELS	0.94 (±0.05)	0.74 (±0.24)	1.0 (±0.00)	0.83 (±0.06)	0.68 (±0.23)	0.96 (±0.04)	0.74 (±0.06)	0.68 (±0.19)	0.86 (±0.12)	0.76 (±0.05)	0.69 (±0.19)	0.92 (±0.08)	0.97 (±0.03)	0.80 (±0.21)	1.0 (±0.00)
Greedy Tree	0.96 (±0.01)	0.94 (±0.03)	0.99 (±0.02)	0.90 (±0.02)	0.85 (±0.04)	0.96 (±0.02)	0.86 (±0.03)	0.83 (±0.03)	0.90 (±0.06)	0.83 (±0.03)	0.81 (±0.03)	0.88 (±0.08)	0.98 (±0.01)	0.97 (±0.01)	1.0 (±0.00)
C4.5 Tree	0.97 (±0.01)	0.94 (±0.02)	1.0 (±0.00)	0.90 (±0.01)	0.85 (±0.03)	0.97 (±0.02)	0.87 (±0.03)	0.82 (±0.02)	0.94 (±0.06)	0.84 (±0.03)	0.82 (±0.04)	0.88 (±0.08)	0.98 (±0.01)	0.97 (±0.01)	1.0 (±0.00)
Bayesian Rule List	0.94 (±0.01)	0.89 (±0.02)	1.0 (±0.00)	0.85 (±0.03)	0.77 (±0.04)	1.0 (±0.00)	0.78 (±0.03)	0.70 (±0.03)	1.0 (±0.01)	0.81 (±0.05)	0.73 (±0.06)	0.99 (±0.01)	0.97 (±0.00)	0.94 (±0.00)	1.0 (±0.00)
Boosted Rules	0.94 (±0.01)	0.89 (±0.02)	1.0 (±0.00)	0.85 (±0.03)	0.78 (±0.04)	0.98 (±0.02)	0.78 (±0.02)	0.70 (±0.03)	0.96 (±0.04)	0.79 (±0.03)	0.80 (±0.08)	0.81 (±0.10)	0.96 (±0.01)	0.93 (±0.02)	1.0 (±0.00)
Slipper	0.92 (±0.03)	0.84 (±0.07)	1.0 (±0.00)	0.77 (±0.05)	0.79 (±0.06)	0.71 (±0.14)	0.69 (±0.05)	0.89 (±0.07)	0.43 (±0.11)	0.75 (±0.07)	0.88 (±0.03)	0.58 (±0.15)	0.92 (±0.09)	0.84 (±0.09)	1.0 (±0.00)

TABLE VIII. WB WITH OVERSAMPLING

Classifier	Time in sec.									
	Grade A		Grade B		Grade C		Grade D		Grade F	
	Train	Test								
CORELS	0.0540 (±0.0053)	0.0006 (±0.0001)	0.0456 (±0.0058)	0.0006 (±0.0002)	0.0475 (±0.0047)	0.0006 (±0.0003)	0.0469 (±0.0108)	0.0004 (±0.0001)	1.6690 (±1.3231)	0.0011 (±0.0009)
Greedy Tree	0.0036 (±0.0014)	0.0023 (±0.0007)	0.0073 (±0.0082)	0.0026 (±0.0015)	0.0042 (±0.0016)	0.0022 (±0.0006)	0.0038 (±0.2265)	0.0024 (±0.0007)	0.0035 (±0.0012)	0.0024 (±0.0008)
C4.5 Tree	1.1081 (±0.1544)	0.0085 (±0.0035)	1.7746 (±0.2468)	0.0113 (±0.0038)	1.8600 (±0.1238)	0.0117 (±0.0010)	1.5420 (±0.2265)	0.0093 (±0.0007)	1.0215 (±0.2051)	0.0077 (±0.0026)
BRL	18.4103 (±2.4006)	0.1596 (±0.0091)	19.4687 (±1.8279)	0.1336 (±0.0075)	1378.9996 (±2710.32)	0.1285 (±0.0099)	21.9118 (±2.7820)	0.1281 (±0.0124)	15.4696 (±1.8045)	0.1621 (±0.0163)
Boosted Rules	0.0137 (±0.0020)	0.0317 (±0.00324)	0.0148 (±0.0044)	0.0320 (±0.00199)	0.0161 (±0.0050)	0.0382 (±0.0063)	0.0614 (±0.0935)	0.0152 (±0.1190)	0.0160 (±0.0025)	0.0354 (±0.0050)
Slipper	146.633 (±215.272)	0.02814 (±0.0090)	152.67 (±220.28)	0.0229 (±0.0011)	37.1966 (±7.8914)	0.0253 (±0.0039)	150.98 (±217.499)	0.0243 (±0.0007)	42.8454 (±5.2960)	0.0207 (±0.0006)

TABLE IX. TRAIN AND TEST TIMES FOR THE WB MODELS

Classifier	Grade A			Grade B			Grade C			Grade D			Grade F		
	Acc.	Prec.	Rec.												
NB	0.90 (±0.03)	0.49 (±0.08)	1.0 (±0.00)	0.65 (±0.16)	0.40 (±0.08)	0.82 (±0.06)	0.73 (±0.06)	0.55 (±0.14)	0.31 (±0.14)	0.78 (±0.05)	0.61 (±0.05)	0.77 (±0.11)	0.93 (±0.00)	0.48 (±0.09)	0.91 (±0.08)
SVM	0.93 (±0.02)	0.71 (±0.37)	0.30 (±0.17)	0.77 (±0.04)	0.0 (±0.00)	0.0 (±0.00)	0.75 (±0.05)	0.90 (±0.20)	0.14 (±0.05)	0.80 (±0.04)	0.76 (±0.08)	0.56 (±0.11)	0.93 (±0.03)	0.25 (±0.22)	0.15 (±0.13)
KNN	0.91 (±0.02)	0.59 (±0.33)	0.27 (±0.05)	0.78 (±0.05)	0.54 (±0.09)	0.45 (±0.09)	0.77 (±0.05)	0.66 (±0.04)	0.48 (±0.10)	0.80 (±0.03)	0.70 (±0.03)	0.64 (±0.07)	0.93 (±0.02)	0.37 (±0.22)	0.27 (±0.20)
Random Forest	0.91 (±0.03)	0.52 (±0.34)	0.35 (±0.19)	0.79 (±0.06)	0.54 (±0.05)	0.43 (±0.09)	0.80 (±0.02)	0.67 (±0.07)	0.60 (±0.05)	0.77 (±0.06)	0.63 (±0.09)	0.65 (±0.09)	0.95 (±0.01)	0.51 (±0.27)	0.36 (±0.19)
Gradient Boosting	0.90 (±0.03)	0.38 (±0.25)	0.63 (±0.41)	0.83 (±0.03)	0.63 (±0.04)	0.62 (±0.06)	0.81 (±0.03)	0.71 (±0.07)	0.59 (±0.09)	0.80 (±0.04)	0.71 (±0.06)	0.67 (±0.07)	0.91 (±0.02)	0.42 (±0.08)	1.0 (±0.00)

TABLE X. BB RESULTS WITHOUT OVERSAMPLING

Classifier	Grade A			Grade B			Grade C			Grade D			Grade F		
	Acc.	Prec.	Rec.												
NB	0.94 (±0.05)	0.74 (±0.23)	1.0 (±0.00)	0.74 (±0.10)	0.61 (±0.29)	0.90 (±0.03)	0.68 (±0.07)	0.71 (±0.21)	0.53 (±0.13)	0.77 (±0.04)	0.70 (±0.17)	0.81 (±0.09)	0.97 (±0.03)	0.80 (±0.21)	1.0 (±0.00)
SVM	0.94 (±0.05)	0.73 (±0.24)	1.0 (±0.00)	0.79 (±0.07)	0.65 (±0.25)	0.96 (±0.06)	0.71 (±0.05)	0.67 (±0.22)	0.80 (±0.09)	0.76 (±0.04)	0.68 (±0.19)	0.92 (±0.08)	0.96 (±0.04)	0.78 (±0.25)	1.0 (±0.00)
KNN	0.91 (±0.05)	0.71 (±0.27)	0.97 (±0.02)	0.76 (±0.05)	0.66 (±0.26)	0.88 (±0.08)	0.73 (±0.03)	0.67 (±0.21)	0.79 (±0.02)	0.79 (±0.06)	0.71 (±0.18)	0.86 (±0.04)	0.96 (±0.02)	0.81 (±0.20)	0.99 (±0.01)
Random Forest	0.95 (±0.03)	0.80 (±0.19)	0.99 (±0.01)	0.88 (±0.07)	0.73 (±0.21)	0.96 (±0.03)	0.86 (±0.04)	0.78 (±0.14)	0.89 (±0.04)	0.83 (±0.07)	0.73 (±0.17)	0.86 (±0.07)	0.98 (±0.02)	0.84 (±0.18)	1.0 (±0.00)
Gradient Boosting	0.94 (±0.04)	0.75 (±0.22)	0.99 (±0.01)	0.80 (±0.03)	0.69 (±0.23)	0.90 (±0.04)	0.78 (±0.07)	0.72 (±0.18)	0.85 (±0.07)	0.78 (±0.05)	0.71 (±0.19)	0.87 (±0.08)	0.97 (±0.03)	0.81 (±0.20)	1.0 (±0.00)

TABLE XI. BB RESULTS WITH OVERSAMPLING

Classifier	Time in sec.									
	Grade A		Grade B		Grade C		Grade D		Grade F	
	Train	Test	Train	Test	Train	Test	Train	Test	Train	Test
NB	0.0034 (±0.0020)	0.0024 (±0.0012)	0.0035 (±0.0021)	0.0024 (±0.0010)	0.0033 (±0.0013)	0.0026 (±0.0010)	0.0029 (±0.0013)	0.0025 (±0.0013)	0.0032 (±0.0014)	0.0026 (±0.0011)
SVM	0.0098 (±0.00618)	0.0046 (±0.0017)	0.0118 (±0.0047)	0.0065 (±0.0019)	0.0119 (±0.0047)	0.0065 (±0.0016)	0.0090 (±0.0037)	0.0050 (±0.0012)	0.0071 (±0.0029)	0.0040 (±0.0011)
KNN	0.0038 (±0.0037)	0.0076 (±0.0030)	0.0026 (±0.0006)	0.0067 (±0.0012)	0.0023 (±0.0003)	0.0056 (±0.0008)	0.0028 (±0.0015)	0.0068 (±0.0036)	0.0027 (±0.0012)	0.0081 (±0.0044)
Random Forest	0.1095 (±0.0128)	0.0076 (±0.0030)	0.1164 (±0.0129)	0.0114 (±0.0005)	0.1138 (±0.0091)	0.0109 (±0.0006)	0.1109 (±0.0084)	0.0110 (±0.0005)	0.1086 (±0.0119)	0.0113 (±0.0012)
Gradient Boosting	0.0390 (±0.0076)	0.0018 (±0.0003)	0.0373 (±0.0064)	0.0018 (±0.0001)	0.0376 (±0.0075)	0.0019 (±0.0002)	0.0388 (±0.0071)	0.0020 (±0.0003)	0.0452 (±0.0034)	0.0021 (±0.0001)

The largest complexity result indicates better interoperability. Table VI shows that CORELS and BRL are the most interpretable among the WB models. On the other hand, the GreedyTree classifier is the lowest interpretable model. Figure 3 shows that there is a positive relationship

between complexity and classifier accuracy. When a classifier gets higher accuracy, the complexity gets better, except for the boosted classifier, which is fixed. Table IX shows that BRL and CORELS have the best complexity results among the other WB models.

TABLE XII. TRAIN AND TEST TIMES FOR THE BB MODELS

	Complexity				
	Grade A	Grade B	Grade C	Grade D	Grade F
CORELS	1.0 (±0.0)	1.0 (±0.0)	0.8 (±0.2450)	1.0 (±0.0)	1.0 (±0.0)
Greedy Tree	0.0075 (±0.0007)	0.0025 (±0.0003)	0.0029 (±0.0002)	0.0030 (±0.0003)	0.0140 (±0.0023)
C4.5 Tree	0.0267 (±0.0007)	0.0116 (±0.0012)	0.0102 (±0.0007)	0.0114 (±0.0010)	0.0464 (±0.0022)
BRL	0.6599 (±0.2799)	0.5905 (±0.1524)	0.3078 (±0.0640)	0.3733 (±0.0326)	0.8333 (±0.2108)
Boosted Rules	0.2 (±0.0)	0.2 (±0.0)	0.2 (±0.0)	0.2 (±0.0)	0.2 (±0.0)
Slipper	0.0990 (±0.0094)	0.06768 (±0.0087)	0.0804 (±0.0112)	0.0667 (±0.0098)	0.0905 (±0.0105)

Fig. 3. WB models' complexity/accuracy relationship.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper compared the CORELS model with other WB and BB models. The results showed that CORELS outperformed the other WB and BB models. The dataset used in this study was obtained from a public institution in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia. In the future, this comparison is planned to be made on data from more colleges and other universities in Saudi Arabia and other countries. An effective prediction of how students will perform has a significant impact on both learning and teaching. This study offers a comprehensive examination of the efficacy of WB and BB categorization models in forecasting academic grades. While BB models provide decision-making procedures that are not easily understood, the emphasis on BB models brings clarity to the outcomes, which is essential for a wide range of stakeholders. The results of this study show that BB models consistently achieve high accuracy and recall rates, regardless of the anticipated grade category, whether it is an A or an F. Additionally, this study reveals significant variations in the precision and recall rates of particular classifiers while making predictions for grade B, with SVM outperforming NB. These results contribute to the understanding of the relative efficiency of various classifiers in educational settings. Furthermore, this study underscores a notable discrepancy in academic achievement when forecasting grades C or D. The RF

algorithm had better accuracy compared to the others, whereas the NB offered the lowest level of effectiveness. These findings provide crucial information on the most reliable models for predicting grades within a specific range, which could provide insight to educational institutions aiming to enhance their classification systems. Furthermore, the data highlights the higher recall of RF in predicting grade C and the usefulness of SVM in predicting grade D. These distinctions offer useful information to schools seeking to improve their forecast accuracy for particular grade categories. This study provides practical insights that can be directly applied to improve grading prediction systems in similar educational situations, by utilizing actual educational data as the basis for analysis.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. A. Mengash, "Using Data Mining Techniques to Predict Student Performance to Support Decision Making in University Admission Systems," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 55462–55470, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2981905>.
- [2] S. E. Sorour, S. A. El Rahman, S. A. Kahouf, and T. Mine, "Understandable Prediction Models of Student Performance Using an Attribute Dictionary," in *Advances in Web-Based Learning-ICWL 2016: 15th International Conference*, Rome, Italy, Oct. 2016, pp. 161–171.
- [3] A. Tarik, H. Aissa, and F. Yousef, "Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning to Predict Student Performance during the COVID-19," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 184, pp. 835–840, Jan. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2021.03.104>.
- [4] P. Dabhade, R. Agarwal, K. P. Alameen, A. T. Fathima, R. Sridharan, and G. Gopakumar, "Educational data mining for predicting students' academic performance using machine learning algorithms," *Materials Today: Proceedings*, vol. 47, pp. 5260–5267, Jan. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2021.05.646>.
- [5] I. Đ. Babić, "Machine learning methods in predicting the student academic motivation," *Croatian Operational Research Review*, pp. 443–461, Dec. 2017.
- [6] A. Cano and J. D. Leonard, "Interpretable Multiview Early Warning System Adapted to Underrepresented Student Populations," *IEEE Transactions on Learning Technologies*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 198–211, Apr. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TLT.2019.2911079>.
- [7] M. Tsiakmaki, G. Kostopoulos, S. Kotsiantis, and O. Ragos, "Fuzzy-based Active Learning for Predicting Student Academic Performance," in *Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Engineering & MIS 2020*, New York, NY, USA, Jun. 2020, Art. no. 87, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3410352.3410823>.
- [8] F. D. Pereira *et al.*, "Explaining Individual and Collective Programming Students' Behavior by Interpreting a Black-Box Predictive Model," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 117097–117119, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3105956>.
- [9] R. Alamri and B. Alharbi, "Explainable Student Performance Prediction Models: A Systematic Review," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 33132–33143, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3061368>.
- [10] W. Xing, R. Guo, E. Petakovic, and S. Goggins, "Participation-based student final performance prediction model through interpretable Genetic Programming: Integrating learning analytics, educational data

- mining and theory," *Computers in Human Behavior*, vol. 47, pp. 168–181, Jun. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2014.09.034>.
- [11] J. Bravo-Agapito, S. J. Romero, and S. Pamplona, "Early prediction of undergraduate Student's academic performance in completely online learning: A five-year study," *Computers in Human Behavior*, vol. 115, Feb. 2021, Art. no. 106595, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2020.106595>.
- [12] W. Zhang, Y. Zhou, and B. Yi, "An Interpretable Online Learner's Performance Prediction Model Based on Learning Analytics," in *Proceedings of the 11th International Conference on Education Technology and Computers*, New York, NY, USA, Jan. 2020, pp. 148–154, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3369255.3369277>.
- [13] J. Xu, K. H. Moon, and M. van der Schaar, "A Machine Learning Approach for Tracking and Predicting Student Performance in Degree Programs," *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 742–753, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1109/JSTSP.2017.2692560>.
- [14] A. Cano, A. Zafra, and S. Ventura, "An interpretable classification rule mining algorithm," *Information Sciences*, vol. 240, pp. 1–20, Aug. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2013.03.038>.
- [15] J. Gu and V. Tresp, "Semantics for Global and Local Interpretation of Deep Neural Networks," arXiv, Oct. 20, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1910.09085>.
- [16] E. Angelino, N. Larus-Stone, D. Alabi, M. Seltzer, and C. Rudin, "Learning Certifiably Optimal Rule Lists," in *Proceedings of the 23rd ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, New York, NY, USA, May 2017, pp. 35–44, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3097983.3098047>.
- [17] L. Calvet Liñán and Á. A. Juan Pérez, "Educational Data Mining and Learning Analytics: differences, similarities, and time evolution," *RUSC. Universities and Knowledge Society Journal*, vol. 12, no. 3, Jul. 2015, Art. no. 98, <https://doi.org/10.7238/rusc.v12i3.2515>.
- [18] M. Langer *et al.*, "What do we want from Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI)? – A stakeholder perspective on XAI and a conceptual model guiding interdisciplinary XAI research," *Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 296, Jul. 2021, Art. no. 103473, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.artint.2021.103473>.
- [19] C. B. Azodi, J. Tang, and S.-H. Shiu, "Opening the Black Box: Interpretable Machine Learning for Geneticists," *Trends in Genetics*, vol. 36, no. 6, pp. 442–455, Jun. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tig.2020.03.005>.
- [20] C. Romero and S. Ventura, "Educational Data Mining: A Review of the State of the Art," *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics, Part C (Applications and Reviews)*, vol. 40, no. 6, pp. 601–618, Aug. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSMCC.2010.2053532>.
- [21] "Statement on Algorithmic Transparency and Accountability," ACM US Public Policy Office, New York, NY, USA, Jan. 2017.
- [22] C. Rudin, "Stop explaining black box machine learning models for high stakes decisions and use interpretable models instead," *Nature Machine Intelligence*, vol. 1, no. 5, pp. 206–215, May 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42256-019-0048-x>.
- [23] T. P. Minh, H. B. Duc, and V. D. Quoc, "Analysis of Leakage Inductances in Shunt Reactors: Application to High Voltage Transmission Lines," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 8488–8491, Jun. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4826>.
- [24] N. L. Tran and T. H. Nguyen, "Reliability Assessment of Steel Plane Frame's Buckling Strength Considering Semi-rigid Connections," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 5099–5103, Feb. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3231>.
- [25] H. Basarudin *et al.*, "Evaluation of Climate Change Effects on Rain Rate Distribution in Malaysia using Hydro-Estimator for 5G and Microwave Links," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 11064–11069, Aug. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5552>.
- [26] N. N. Long, N. H. Quyet, N. X. Tung, B. T. Thanh, and T. N. Hoa, "Damage Identification of Suspension Footbridge Structures using New Hunting-based Algorithms," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 11085–11090, Aug. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5983>.

Arabic Sentiment Analysis for Student Evaluation using Machine Learning and the AraBERT Transformer

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ABSTRACT

Recently, Sentiment Analysis (SA) has become a crucial area of research as it enables us to gauge people's opinions from various sources such as student evaluations, social media posts, product reviews, etc. This paper aims to create an Arabic dataset derived from student satisfaction surveys conducted at the University of Jeddah regarding their subjects and instructors. In addition, this study presents an evaluation of classical machine learning models such as Naive Bayes, Support Vector Machine, Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, and Random Forest classifier for Arabic SA, whereas the results are compared using various metrics. Furthermore, AraBERT was used for the pre-trained transformer to improve the performance, achieving an accuracy of 78%. The paper fills the lack of SA research in the education domain in the Arabic language.

Keywords-sentiment analysis; natural language processing; machine learning; pre-trained transformer

I. INTRODUCTION

Sentiment Analysis (SA) is a Natural Language Processing (NLP) application that analyzes the words in a sentence using linguistic and textual assessment to classify the sentiments, often into positive, negative, or neutral [1]. SA approaches can be classified into two main classes [2, 3]: The Lexicon-Based Approach and the Machine Learning-Based Approach. The Lexicon-Based Approach uses a sentiment dictionary to classify the sentiment, which is a collection of a group of lexical units accompanied by their emotional orientation. The Machine Learning approach uses machine learning algorithms such as Naïve Bayes (NB), Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Logistic Regression (LR). Furthermore, there have been some studies that have explored hybrid approaches, combining lexicon and corpus techniques [4]. SA is useful for many applications, including social media, customer reviews, education, instruction evaluations, etc.

Arabic is a national language and it differs from other languages in structure. It is morphologically rich, and has multiple dialects, which makes it more difficult for NLP and requires some pre-processing. The Arabic language is written from right to left and has 28 letters, including 3 vowels. Also, it has diacritics which are used to distinguish between words that have the same letters but differ in meaning. For example, the word "علم" has more than one meanings, "عَلِمَ" that means science, "عَلَّمَ" that means flag, or "عَلِمَ" that means known [5]. Also, some pronouns are related to the word, such as "سيعلمونه" that means "they will teach him". For that, there are some challenges in Arabic language processing which are summarized in [6].

In this work, we employ machine learning algorithms namely SVM, NB, LR, Decision Tree (DT), and Random Forest (RF). Also, we apply the AraBERT model to improve the result of Arabic SA on our dataset that is collected from the students of the University of Jeddah.

II. RELATED WORKS

There are several research studies of SA in different languages and techniques. We summarize some of them in this section.

A. Classical Machine Learning Approaches

Author in [7] employed Discriminative Multinomial Naïve Bayes (DMNB) to improve the performance of Arabic SA and compared the result with other machine learning algorithms in the same dataset. The dataset contains 2,000 Arabic tweets

classified as positive or negative. The accuracy is 87.5%, which is better than that of the other algorithms. The aim in [8] is to create a dataset from a student survey written in Spanish and classify it into positive, negative, and neutral. The dataset contains 2,925 rows. The authors use two learning algorithms: SVM and LR with different feature extraction techniques. They found the best result, which is 72.6%, when they used an LR model with bi-grams and tri-grams. Authors in [9] trained an SVM classifier for students' feedback documents in mixed languages (Indonesian and English). The dataset was created from student surveys. There were 636 documents annotated as positive, negative, and neutral. The accuracy of this work is 74%. Additionally, within [10], the Amazon platform was employed to conduct SA on product reviews. This analysis utilized LR and DT algorithms on a dataset consisting of 4,960 reviews for Titan Men watches written in English, with the objective of classifying them as either positive or negative. The results indicated an accuracy of 99% for DT and 94% for LR.

B. Deep Learning Approaches

There are several studies that use Deep Learning (DL) algorithms. Authors in [11] compared Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), and used them together. They were applied on the semEval dataset, which contains 32,000 English tweets. The results of the CNN model were similar to the results of LSTM, but the results were better when they were used together. Authors in [12] used Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) for SA and product review classification. They collected more than 5,000 reviews from Bangla e-commerce sites written in Bangla dialect, which were annotated as good or bad and as complaint, recommended, wrong delivery, and appreciation. The achieved accuracy was 84% for SA and 69% for product classification. Authors in [13] introduced a novel approach known as the Adaptive Particle Grey Wolf Optimizer with Deep Learning-based Sentiment Analysis (APGWO-DLSA) to effectively categorize sentiments within product reviews. This method was applied to two distinct datasets: Cell Phones And Accessories (CPAA) and Amazon Products (AP), both aimed at distinguishing between positive and negative sentiments. In CPAA dataset, consisting of 100,000 reviews, their method yielded an impressive accuracy of 94.77%, while in the AP dataset, comprising of 14,000 reviews, it achieved an accuracy of 85.31%.

Regarding the Arabic language, authors in [14] applied LSTM to enhance the prediction accuracy for Arabic SA. They used the Large-Scale Arabic Book Reviews (LABR) dataset, which contains 14,448 reviews labeled as 0 and 1 for negative

and positive. The accuracy was 82%. Some researchers applied machine learning and DL algorithms [15, 16]. SVM was used as a baseline in [15] and was compared with four DL models (LSTM, LSTM +CNN, GRU, and GRU+CNN). The authors aimed to identify Arabic hate speech on Twitter. They collected 11,000 tweets labeled into five categories (none, religious, racial, sexism, or general hate). The best accuracy achieved was 72% when using CNN with LSTM. In [16], the author analyzes instructor evaluation reviews for SA. The author uses five machine learning algorithms: NB, SVM, LR, k-nearest-neighbors (KNN), and RF along with various ensemble learning techniques. He also employed five DL algorithms: CNN, RNN, bidirectional RNN-AM, GRU, and LSTM, with different word embeddings. The dataset used contained 154,000 reviews that were collected from popular instructor review websites and were labeled as positive or negative. The best accuracy was 98.29%, when using RNN with GloVe word embedding. Authors in [17] applied NB, LR, and SVM, which achieved the highest accuracy of 63%. They improved the accuracy to 70% by applying LSTM, which is a DL algorithm, using an Arabic dataset containing 32,186 tweets that were classified as positive, negative, and neutral.

C. The AraBERT Pre-trained Transformer

AraBERT is the first Arabic transformer model. It was built based on the BERT transformer model that was developed by Google. The AraBERT model was trained on a huge dataset of the modern standard Arabic language and various Arabic dialects, and it was evaluated on several downstream tasks, including SA, Named Entity Recognition, and Question Answering, which has helped advance the field of Arabic NLP [18]. AraBERT is designed to overcome the challenges of Arabic language processing, such as the presence of dialects, multiple negations, and compound words. It is able to understand the context and meaning of Arabic text, which makes it valuable for businesses and organizations seeking to understand their customers' opinions and emotions. It is a powerful tool in the field of Arabic NLP, which has been shown to achieve state-of-the-art results on various Arabic NLP tasks. Recently, BERT and AraBERT have been used in several NLP and SA researches, e.g. in [19] the authors built their Arabic BERT approach based on the BERT model to overcome challenges related to the Arabic language. They applied it on five different datasets and compared the results with classical machine learning and DL algorithms that have been used in the same datasets in previous works. Similarly, in [20], several machine learning algorithms and AraBERT were employed on various datasets from different domains, including restaurant, movies, and product reviews. Additionally, authors in [21] utilized the AraBERT model to analyze the comments and reviews on different websites using the ARev dataset, which contains 40,000 Arabic reviews classified as positive or negative. Their approach achieved an accuracy of 92.5%

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

In this paper, we present machine learning algorithms that were previously employed on an Arabic dataset to classify sentiments into positive, negative, or neutral. However, the performance of these algorithms falls short when compared to

other works, due to the unique nature of the Arabic language. To address this issue, we employ the use of the pre-trained AraBERT model, which has been fine-tuned specifically for the Arabic language. The proposed methodology is outlined in Figure 1. We collected the dataset from a student survey, then we applied preprocessing to clean the data. After that, we employed the machine learning algorithms SVM, NB, LR, DT, and RF along with the AraBERT pre-trained model. Finally, we compared the performances of the applied models based on accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score and ROC-AUC.

Fig. 1. The proposed methodology.

A. Dataset

We created the dataset from a student survey that was filled out at the end of every semester by the students at the University of Jeddah. The survey is provided by the university system and it is a requirement for academic accreditation. There are three steps in creating our dataset: Text Extraction, Data Cleaning, and Annotating. The student survey contains two sections: subject evaluation and instructor of the subject evaluation. Each section has two types of questions: open and closed questions. Questions and answers are written in the Arabic language. Firstly, we extracted the text to build our dataset from the answers to open questions. The open questions for the subject evaluation are:

- What do you like about this subject?
- What you do not like about this subject?
- What are your suggestions to improve this subject?

While the open questions for instructor evaluation are:

- What aspects of instructor's activity helped students learn?
- What aspects of instructor's activity needs to improve to help students learn?

We received 1,044 responses from students of the University of Jeddah. Hence, the number of comments we got is 5,220.

Many of the comments are not useful, such as blank fields, opaque letters, etc. We removed these comments from the dataset and its size became 3,472 rows after cleaning. Additionally, there are a few non-Arabic comments that were translated into Arabic. Finally, each row in the dataset was manually labeled as positive, negative, or neutral by native Arabic speakers. The distribution of our dataset was: 1,651 positive, 1,270 negative, and 551 neutral comments, as shown in Figure 2. Table I provides a sample of the dataset.

TABLE I. SAMPLE OF OUR DATASET

Negative	الماده جدا صعبيه واللغه جديده على معظم الطلاب وتحتاج جهد واحنا اغلبنا خريجين وساعاتنا مليانه وفوق كذا مافي تشجيع من الاستاذ هتهدد بالترسيب والحرمان وتحطم الطالبية في نطقها لو جاوبت غلط ودايما تهزى في مستوى الطالبات
Negative	تنقيص الدرجات و عدم مراعات مشاعر الطالبات
Positive	جميع الاشياء كويسة
Positive	اسلوب الاستاذة ساعد ف فهم المقرر كثيرا

Fig. 2. The dataset classes.

B. Pre-processing

Data pre-processing is an important step in NLP that cleans all noisy characters from the text and additions in some words that negatively affect the results. It is done through removing noise, normalization, and stemming. The removing list consists of:

- Punctuations and special characters.
- Numbers.
- English characters and repeat characters.
- Stop words like (أما ، إن ، ايك ، اذاء ايك).

Arabic Normalization: standardizes the spelling of some letters like Alef and Hamza by replacing all (أ, إ, ؤ) into (ا, إ, ؤ), (ئ, ؤ) into (ئ, ؤ) and others.

Additionally, during the pre-processing step, stemming was applied to each word. Stemming is the process of removing suffixes/prefixes and reducing words to their root or base form. For example, the word "حركات" becomes "حرك" after word stemming by using the ISRIStemmer stemming algorithm.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We split the dataset into 80% and 20% for training and validation, respectively. We employed five machine learning classifiers and the AraBERT model using the scikit-learn library for machine learning and AraBERT library. TF-IDF feature extraction was applied that refers to term frequency-inverse document frequency. It calculates a weight for each word that shows the importance of this word based on the number of times it appears. We used the standard performance metrics precision, recall, f-score, and accuracy to evaluate our work:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad (1)$$

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (2)$$

$$F1 = 2 \times \frac{Recall \times Precision}{Recall+Precision} \quad (3)$$

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \quad (4)$$

where TP stands for True Positive, FP for False Positive, TN for True Negative, and FN for False Negative.

In addition, the performance of the models was evaluated using the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve and the Area Under the Curve (AUC). The ROC curve provides a visual representation of the performance of a classification model across all classification thresholds by plotting the True Positive Rate (TPR) and False Positive Rate (FPR), which are calculated by (5) and (6). The AUC quantifies the entire two-dimensional area under the ROC curve as a metric of performance.

$$TPR = \frac{TP}{(TP + FN)} \quad (5)$$

$$FPR = \frac{FP}{FP+TN} \quad (6)$$

A. Re-sampling Dataset

When there is unequal distribution of the classes in a dataset, it is called imbalanced. This can affect the results of machine learning models. There are several methods to handle this problem including Over-Sampling and Under-Sampling [22]. Over-sampling involves adding some samples to the minority class, while under-sampling involves removing samples from the majority class. We used these two techniques to obtain a balanced dataset. We applied the Random Over-Sampling on the "neutral" class, which originally had 551 samples and it and at the end 1,649 samples. Then, we applied the Random Under-Sampling for "neutral" and "positive" classes. Their size became 1,271. Figure 3 shows the dataset classes before and after re-sampling. We encode the target variable so the label becomes [0: "negative", 1: "neutral", 2: "positive"].

Fig. 3. Dataset before and after re-sampling.

B. Machine Learning Algorithms

1) Support Vector Machine

SVM is a classification algorithm for linear and nonlinear data that builds a decision boundary (hyperplane) to classify two classes [23]. The SVM algorithm's formula can be represented mathematically as an optimization problem: Given a set of training data (x_i, y_i) , $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, where x_i is a feature vector and y_i is the corresponding label, the goal is to find the optimal hyperplane that separates the data into classes. This is done by minimizing the following objective function [24]:

$$\min_{\frac{1}{2}} \|w\|^2 + C * \text{sum}(\max(0.1 - y_i * (w \cdot x_i + b))) \quad (7)$$

where $\|w\|^2$ is the square of the Euclidean norm of the weight vector w , C is the regularization parameter, which determines the trade-off between maximizing the margin and minimizing the training errors (we set $C=1$ in our experiment), $w \cdot x_i + b$ is the linear equation of the hyperplane, $y_i * (w \cdot x_i + b)$ is the decision function, which returns positive values for samples that lie on the one side of the hyperplane and negative values for samples that lie on the other side, and $\max(\cdot)$ is the hinge loss function, which is used to penalize samples that are misclassified. The resulting hyperplane can be used to make predictions on new data. The result of our SVM experiment is shown in Table II.

TABLE II. CLASSIFICATION REPORT OF SVM

	Imbalanced Data			Balanced Data		
	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Precision	Recall	F1-score
Neutral	0.61	0.41	0.49	0.64	0.72	0.68
Negative	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.69	0.61	0.64
Positive	0.74	0.83	0.78	0.64	0.64	0.64
Accuracy	0.72			0.66		

2) Naïve Bayes

NB is based on the Bayes theorem that is the probability of the existence of a class based on a given text. It is a supervised learning algorithm used for classification problems [25]. There are more than one versions of NB which are MultinomialNB, BernoulliNB, CategoricalNB, ComplementNB, and GaussianNB. We used MultinomialNB because it most suitable for text classification. Let's consider a text comment x with N words and let's assume there are 3 classes in our sentiment analysis problem. For a given comment x and a class y , the probability that the comment belongs to class y is calculated as follows:

$$P(y|x) = \frac{P(x|y) * P(y)}{P(x)} \quad (8)$$

where $P(y|x)$ is the posterior probability of class y given the text x . $P(x|y)$ is the likelihood of observing the text x given class y . $P(y)$ is the prior probability of class y . $P(x)$ is the evidence, which is the probability of observing the text x regardless of the class. It is applied to each class to calculate the posterior probability for each class, and the class with the highest probability can be selected as the predicted class for the document x . Table III shows the result of our experiment for MultinomialNB.

TABLE III. CLASSIFICATION REPORT OF MULTINOMIALNB

	Imbalanced Data			Balanced Data		
	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Precision	Recall	F1-score
Neutral	0.72	0.20	0.31	0.60	0.74	0.66
Negative	0.71	0.69	0.70	0.72	0.57	0.64
Positive	0.67	0.85	0.75	0.66	0.65	0.66
Accuracy	0.68			0.65		

3) Logistic Regression

LR is a linear classification that is a statistical model for solving classification problems [26]. It aims to learn the

relationship between the data. For a given comment as a vector feature x and its sentiment y , the LR model is defined as:

$$p(y = 1|x) = \frac{1}{(1 + \exp(-z))} \quad (1)$$

$$z = w_0 + w_1 x_1 + w_2 x_2 + \dots + w_n x_n \quad (2)$$

where $p(y = 1|x)$ is the predicted probability that $y = 1$, given x , z is the linear combination of features and coefficients, and W_i is the weight assigned to feature x_i .

The goal of training an LR model is to learn the weights w_i that maximize the likelihood of the observed data. The prediction for a new sample is made by computing the predicted probability $p(y = 1|x)$, and the class label is assigned as 1 if $p(y = 1|x)$ is greater than or equal to 0.5. Also in scikit-learn, it has a C parameter like in SVM. We set it equal to [0.01, 0.1, 1, 10, 100] and then find the optimal hyperparameter using GridSearchCV. The result of LR is shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV. CLASSIFICATION REPORT OF LR

	Imbalanced Data			Balanced Data		
	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Precision	Recall	F1-score
Neutral	0.67	0.37	0.48	0.64	0.88	0.71
Negative	0.73	0.69	0.71	0.77	0.63	0.70
Positive	0.71	0.85	0.77	0.67	0.64	0.65
Accuracy	0.71			0.69		

4) Decision Tree

DT is useful for classification problems. It aims to predict the values by simple decision rules [27]. It works by recursively dividing the data into smaller subsets based on the values of the input features, until the subsets contain only samples of the same class or the samples are homogeneous with respect to the target variable. The tree structure is used to represent the decisions and their consequences. A DT can be represented by a series of decision rules, each represented by a node in the tree. At each node, a test is performed on one of the input features, and based on the test results, the sample is either sent to the left or right child node. The process is repeated until a terminal node (also known as a leaf node) is reached. We set all hyperparameters to their default values except for 'criterion,' which is set to 'entropy' to measure the quality of a split. Table V shows the results.

TABLE V. THE CLASSIFICATION REPORT OF DT

	Imbalanced Data			Balanced Data		
	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Precision	Recall	F1-score
Neutral	0.45	0.47	0.46	0.65	0.88	0.75
Negative	0.64	0.63	0.63	0.69	0.56	0.62
Positive	0.72	0.71	0.71	0.64	0.54	0.58
Accuracy	0.64			0.66		

5) Random Forest

RF algorithm is used for classification problems. It consists of multiple DTs, and it can improve the accuracy of the DT algorithm [28]. The basic idea behind RF is to randomly sample the training data with replacement (bootstrapping) and fit multiple DTs to the bootstrapped samples. The final

prediction is made by taking a majority vote in the predictions of all the trees by taking a majority vote in the classification problems based on the predictions of all the trees. Table VI shows the results of random forest classifier [29].

TABLE VI. CLASSIFICATION REPORT OF RF

	Imbalanced Data			Balanced Data		
	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Precision	Recall	F1-score
Neutral	0.60	0.45	0.52	0.72	0.89	0.80
Negative	0.73	0.72	0.73	0.77	0.60	0.68
Positive	0.74	0.81	0.77	0.68	0.68	0.68
Accuracy	0.72			0.72		

C. AraBERT

AraBERT is a pre-trained language model developed by OpenAI for NLP tasks in the Arabic language. The basic architecture of AraBERT [21] consists of multi-layer transformer blocks and includes a deep bidirectional encoding mechanism, where each word is encoded based on the context from both the left and right sides of the word. In SA, the final hidden state of the AraBERT network is typically used to predict the sentiment of a given text by passing it through a linear layer followed by a softmax activation function to generate a probability distribution over the predefined sentiment classes. The classification report of our experiments for the AraBERT model is shown in Table VII.

Fig. 4. ROC Curve for the imbalanced dataset: a) SVM, b) MultinomialNB, c) LR, d) DT, e) RF, f) AraBERT.

Fig. 5. ROC Curve for the balanced dataset: a) SVM, b) MultinomialNB, c) LR, d) DT, e) RF, f) AraBERT.

TABLE VII. CLASSIFICATION REPORT OF ARABERT

	Imbalanced Data			Balanced Data		
	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Precision	Recall	F1-score
Neutral	0.74	0.47	0.57	0.87	0.77	0.82
Negative	0.80	0.85	0.82	0.77	0.80	0.78
Positive	0.85	0.90	0.87	0.79	0.84	0.81
Accuracy	0.82			0.80		

TABLE VIII. THE RESULTS OF THE BALANCED DATASET.

	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-score	AUC
MultinomialNB	0.65	0.65	0.65	0.65	0.81
SVM	0.66	0.66	0.66	0.66	0.81
LR	0.69	0.70	0.69	0.68	0.83
DT	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.66	0.78
RF	0.72	0.73	0.72	0.72	0.87
AraBERT	0.80	0.81	0.80	0.80	0.92

It is a commonly held misconception that the highest accuracy equates to the best performance in a classification problem. However, accuracy alone is not always a suitable metric for evaluating the performance of a model, particularly in the case of imbalanced datasets. The classification reports presented in Tables II-VI demonstrate the results obtained from both balanced and imbalanced datasets. Although the highest accuracy was achieved in the imbalanced dataset, a closer examination of the precision, recall, and F1 scores reveals a bias towards the positive class, with the values of the neutral class being comparatively lower. This is attributed to the variance disparity between classes in the dataset. The ROC curve in Figure 4 further highlights this phenomenon, as it illustrates that the area under the curve for the neutral class is significantly lower than that of the other classes. However, the ROC curve in Figure 5, which represents the balanced dataset, showcases a convergent area under the curve for all classifier models, except for the decision tree and random forest. In this scenario, the area of the neutral class is the highest. Moreover, the balanced dataset distributes the values of precision, recall, and F1 evenly among the neutral, negative, and positive classes. Hence, the results obtained from the balanced dataset, as depicted in Table VIII, are adopted as the preferred.

Several machine learning algorithms and a pre-trained transformer were evaluated for their effectiveness in Arabic SA on both imbalanced and balanced datasets. Among the machine learning algorithms, the RF classifier achieved the highest performance with an accuracy of 72%. The use of the AraBERT model led to a marked improvement in the SA results, as indicated by an accuracy of 80%.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This study conducted a comprehensive comparison of various machine learning models, including SVM, multinomial NB, LR, DT, and RF classifiers, alongside the AraBERT pre-trained model for Arabic sentiment analysis. Our analysis, based on a dataset collected from students at the University of Jeddah, comprising over 3,400 samples categorized into positive, negative, and neutral sentiments, revealed that AraBERT outperformed the other models.

As part of our future research endeavors, we aim to expand our dataset by gathering student evaluations from a diverse array of universities, encompassing different Arabic dialects. Furthermore, we are interested in exploring the incorporation of advanced Deep Learning Models, such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), to further enhance the accuracy and applicability of SA in the Arabic language. These initiatives will help us advance our understanding of sentiment analysis in the Arabic context and contribute to the broader field of natural language processing.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Kennedy, "Perspectives on Sentiment Analysis," *Journal of Broadcasting & Electronic Media*, vol. 56, no. 4, pp. 435–450, Oct. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1080/08838151.2012.732141>.
- [2] F. S. Doliyaniti, D. Iakovakis, S. B. Dias, S. Hadjileontiadou, J. A. Diniz, and L. Hadjileontiadis, "Sentiment Analysis Techniques and Applications in Education: A Survey," in *International Conference on Technology and Innovation in Learning, Teaching and Education*, Thessaloniki, Greece, Jun. 2018, pp. 412–427, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-20954-4_31.
- [3] M. Hilario, D. Esenarro, I. Petrlik, and C. Rodriguez, "Systematic Literature Review of Sentiment Analysis Techniques," *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 506–517, 2021.
- [4] T. Alqurashi, "Arabic Sentiment Analysis for Twitter Data: A Systematic Literature Review," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 10292–10300, Apr. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5662>.
- [5] N. Boudad, R. Faizi, R. Oulad Haj Thami, and R. Chiheb, "Sentiment analysis in Arabic: A review of the literature," *Ain Shams Engineering Journal*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 2479–2490, Dec. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asej.2017.04.007>.
- [6] H. Rahab, M. Djoudi, and A. Zitouni, "Sentiment Analysis of Arabic Documents: Main Challenges and Recent Advances," in *Natural Language Processing for Global and Local Business*, Hershey, PA, USA: IGI Global, 2021, pp. 307–331.
- [7] H. AlSalman, "An Improved Approach for Sentiment Analysis of Arabic Tweets in Twitter Social Media," in *3rd International Conference on Computer Applications & Information Security*, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, Mar. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCAIS48893.2020.9096850>.
- [8] H. Newman and D. Joyner, "Sentiment Analysis of Student Evaluations of Teaching," in *International Conference on Artificial Intelligence in Education*, London, UK, Jun. 2018, pp. 246–250, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-93846-2_45.
- [9] D. F. Sengkey, A. Jacobus, and F. J. Manoppo, "Implementing Support Vector Machine Sentiment Analysis to Students' Opinion toward Lecturer in an Indonesian Public University," *Journal of Sustainable Engineering: Proceedings Series*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 194–198, Sep. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.35793/joseps.v1i2.27>.
- [10] M. A. Kausar, S. O. Fageeri, and A. Soosaimanickam, "Sentiment Classification based on Machine Learning Approaches in Amazon Product Reviews," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 10849–10855, Jun. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5854>.
- [11] D. Goularas and S. Kamis, "Evaluation of Deep Learning Techniques in Sentiment Analysis from Twitter Data," in *International Conference on Deep Learning and Machine Learning in Emerging Applications*, Istanbul, Turkey, Aug. 2019, pp. 12–17, <https://doi.org/10.1109/Deep-ML.2019.00011>.
- [12] M. H. Munna, M. R. I. Rifat, and A. S. M. Badrudduza, "Sentiment Analysis and Product Review Classification in E-commerce Platform," in *23rd International Conference on Computer and Information Technology*, Dhaka, Bangladesh, Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCIT51783.2020.9392710>.

- [13] D. Elangovan and V. Subedha, "Adaptive Particle Grey Wolf Optimizer with Deep Learning-based Sentiment Analysis on Online Product Reviews," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 10989–10993, Jun. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5787>.
- [14] A. Q. Al-Bayati, A. S. Al-Araji, and S. H. Ameen, "Arabic Sentiment Analysis (ASA) Using Deep Learning Approach," *Journal of Engineering*, vol. 26, no. 6, pp. 85–93, Jun. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.31026/j.eng.2020.06.07>.
- [15] A. Al-Hassan and H. Al-Dossari, "Detection of hate speech in Arabic tweets using deep learning," *Multimedia Systems*, vol. 28, no. 6, pp. 1963–1974, Dec. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00530-020-00742-w>.
- [16] A. Onan, "Mining opinions from instructor evaluation reviews: A deep learning approach," *Computer Applications in Engineering Education*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 117–138, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1002/cae.22179>.
- [17] A. Alshutayri *et al.*, "Evaluating sentiment analysis for Arabic Tweets using machine learning and deep learning," *Romanian Journal of Information Technology and Automatic Control*, vol. 32, no. 4, pp. 7–18, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.33436/v32i4y202201>.
- [18] W. Antoun, F. Baly, and H. Hajj, "ArABERT: Transformer-based Model for Arabic Language Understanding," arXiv, Mar. 07, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2003.00104>.
- [19] H. Chouikhi, H. Chniter, and F. Jarray, "Arabic Sentiment Analysis Using BERT Model," in *International Conference on Computational Collective Intelligence*, Rhodes, Greece, Oct. 2021, pp. 621–632, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-88113-9_50.
- [20] R. A. Alsuhemi and S. M. Zurbah, "Machine Learning and AraBERT Models for Arabic Online Reviews Sentiment Analysis," *Romanian Journal of Information Technology and Automatic Control*, pp. 1–14, 2022.
- [21] H. El Moubtahij, H. Abdelali, and E. B. Tazi, "AraBERT transformer model for Arabic comments and reviews analysis," *IAES International Journal of Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 379–387, Mar. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.11591/ijai.v11.i1.pp379-387>.
- [22] "Resampling strategies for imbalanced datasets." <https://kaggle.com/code/rafjaa/resampling-strategies-for-imbalanced-datasets>.
- [23] T. Joachims, "Text categorization with Support Vector Machines: Learning with many relevant features," in *European Conference on Machine Learning*, Chemnitz, Germany, Apr. 1998, pp. 137–142, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BFb0026683>.
- [24] V. Kecman, "Support Vector Machines – An Introduction," in *Support Vector Machines: Theory and Applications*, L. Wang, Ed. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer, 2005, pp. 1–47.
- [25] D. Berrar, "Bayes' Theorem and Naive Bayes Classifier," in *Encyclopedia of Bioinformatics and Computational Biology*, Amsterdam, Netherlands: Elsevier, 2018, pp. 403–412.
- [26] S. T. Indra, L. Wikarsa, and R. Turang, "Using logistic regression method to classify tweets into the selected topics," in *International Conference on Advanced Computer Science and Information Systems*, Malang, Indonesia, Oct. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICACSIS.2016.7872727>.
- [27] B. Charbuty and A. Abdulazez, "Classification Based on Decision Tree Algorithm for Machine Learning," *Journal of Applied Science and Technology Trends*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 20–28, Mar. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.38094/jastt20165>.
- [28] J. L. Speiser, M. E. Miller, J. Tooze, and E. Ip, "A comparison of random forest variable selection methods for classification prediction modeling," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 134, pp. 93–101, Nov. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2019.05.028>.
- [29] L. Breiman, "Random Forests," *Machine Learning*, vol. 45, no. 1, pp. 5–32, Oct. 2001, <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1010933404324>.

Enhancement of Power System Security by the Intelligent Control of a Static Synchronous Series Compensator

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ABSTRACT

Improving and maintaining the stability of a power system is a major focus of modern technology and research. However, due to financial issues, environmental concerns, and health risks associated with electric and magnetic fields, the growth of the current transmission system is constrained. Transmission line problems can be resolved by the effective use of reactive power compensation based on Flexible AC Transmission (FACT) devices. The effectiveness of these devices in regulating active and reactive powers as well as dampening oscillations in the transient phase of the power system is examined using a Static Synchronous Series Compensator (SSSC) with Artificial Neural Network (ANN) control. When compared to the traditional Proportional Integral (PI) controller, the suggested ANN controller offers better dynamic performance. For the suggested test system, this study utilized modeling and simulation using the MATLAB/Simulink software. The observations show that by using ANN in disturbed situations, power oscillations are quickly damped and power flow is enhanced.

Keywords-FACT; SSSC; PI; fuzzy damping of oscillations; ANN; power handling capacity

I. INTRODUCTION

The need for electrical power in the modern world has grown dramatically during the past few decades. Power producing facilities are usually functioning at their utmost capacity to meet the growing demand and transmission lines are likewise approaching their thermal limitations. As a result, power systems appear to be less protected, and they are constantly exposed to voltage instabilities, which have caused several significant network breakdowns throughout the world.

In [1], using MATLAB/Simulink, it was shown that SSSC with POD and ANN has a greater potential for damping network oscillations. Additionally, the real power of the system is increased by SSSC-POD with ANNs, increasing the network's load capacity. In [2], a comparison of STATCOM with the traditional PI controller and a fuzzy-based controller is conducted. The results suggest that the system's dynamic performance is improved by the coordinated function of POD and PSS. Designing an SSSC with the addition of RBFN to the sliding mode technology improves power flow and controls DC voltage in transmission network [3]. Using PI and ANN control techniques with a pod controller, the article compares the efficacy of SSSC in transmission networks. In comparison to the PI controller, the suggested ANN controller may deliver

high dynamic performance [4-6]. The components of the SSSC intelligent fuzzy control have been developed in detail to ensure smooth reactive power regulation in [7]. To synchronise the voltage control of the SSSC and increase stability, fuzzy logic was used in [8, 9]. In [10], and in order to synchronise the control of the SSSC a performance comparison between the PI and the RBFN controllers was conducted. The outcome showed that the SSSC controller based on RBFN is superior to the PI controller. For enhancing STATCOM performance during abrupt, significant disruptions, the usage of a super-capacitor with STATCOM is suggested in [11]. The control of damping of SSSC used in power systems is examined in this [12, 13]. The effectiveness of SSSC, STATCOM, and UPFC for reducing oscillations and stabilising the power system is examined in [14]. The location of SSSC in the test system is determined using the analytical hierarchy approach [15].

Many researchers have studied the SSSC performance under steady state and abnormal system conditions. In this study, when compared to the PI controller, the suggested ANN controller has a higher dynamic performance. For the given test system, this study suggests modeling and simulation with the MATLAB/Simulink software. In comparison with the PI controller, the results show that using ANN under abnormal

situations rapidly damps power oscillation and increases power flow. The PI based SSSC performance deteriorates under changing system conditions, therefore an intelligent controller for SSSC is required. The main contributions of the current paper are:

- Verification of the conventional PI based SSSC performance under steady state as well as disturbing conditions.
- An ANN-based SSSC is designed with two input variables like change in voltage and rate of change in voltage signal for damping the oscillations in fault condition. The local mode of oscillations is analyzed.
- Performance comparison of the SSSC controller for inter area oscillation
- The multimachine model of the sample system is utilized to verify the role of the proposed SSSC controller in MATLAB environment.

II. OVERVIEW OF THE SSSC

The way a series compensator with a voltage source converter able to inject voltage in a transmission line so that the P and Q of the transmission line can be easily managed with help of coupling transformer can be seen in [16].

III. CONTROL SYSTEM OF THE SSSC

Figure 2 represents the SSSC control system. The current I is synchronized by a Phase-Locked Loop (PLL). The result from PLL ($\theta = \omega t$) is utilized to calculate the components of the AC 3Φ voltages and currents named as V_d , V_q or I_d , I_q . The q component of the AC voltages V_1 , V_2 and V_{dc} is monitored by a measuring system. The AC and DC voltage regulators calculate the two converter voltage components (V_{dcnv} and V_{qcnv}) necessary to produce the V_{dcref} and V_{qcref} , i. e. the desired DC voltage and the injected voltage respectively.

Fig. 1. Single-line diagram of the SSSC control system.

IV. MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF THE SSSC

The two bus transmission line shown in Figure 2 has three components: line's resistance (r), it's reactance X , and voltage injection V_c . Figure 3 shows the vector representation of a transmission line.

Fig. 2. Equivalent circuit.

Fig. 3. Phasor diagram.

Equation (1) indicates the transmission line voltage drop:

$$IX - Vc = 2V \sin \frac{\delta}{2} \tag{1}$$

The current equation is:

$$I = \frac{Vc}{X} + \frac{2V \sin \frac{\delta}{2}}{X} \tag{2}$$

Equation (3) gives the active power. The imaginary power of the line is given by (4) and (5) provides the current in the compensator:

$$P = VI \cos \frac{\delta}{2} = \frac{VVc}{X} \cos \frac{\delta}{2} + \frac{V^2}{X} \sin \delta \tag{3}$$

$$Q = VI \sin \frac{\delta}{2} = \frac{VVc}{X} \sin \frac{\delta}{2} + \frac{V^2}{X} (1 - \cos \delta) \tag{4}$$

$$I = \frac{2V \sin \frac{\delta}{2}}{X(1 - Kse)} \tag{5}$$

Power flow can be controlled by changing the injection voltage.

V. TEST POWER SYSTEM MODEL

A SSSC multi-machine test system can be seen in Figure 4. Between buses B1 and B2, a 100 MVA SSSC is attached. There are two important load centers at bus B3 and two power production substations that make up the electrical grid. The first power generating substation (M1) has a 1000 MVA rating, while the second (M2) has a 5000 MVA rating. To simulate the load of about 5000 MW, a dynamic load model is employed. M1 is coupled to the load by lines L1 and L2. In order to construct a three-phase fault, L1 and L2 are 150 km and 700 km long, respectively.

Fig. 4. The test system.

VI. SSSC NEURAL NETWORK CONTROLLER MODELING

An ANN is a versatile tool for creating learning algorithms and decision-making processes that allow for precise regulation of activities in a variety of applications. The ANN approach, which selects what to do for a certain testing input based on the trained data provided, fundamentally relies on the past information provided [16]. The feed forward model is the most fundamental kind of ANN. The following are the basic processes involved in NN controller modeling:

- Step 1: Examine the i/p for the ANN controller.
- Step 2: Decide the ANN type.
- STEP 3: Examine the required output for the ANN controller.

The structure of the suggested ANN controller and the ANN controller simulation block developed after successful development and training are shown in Figures 5 and 6.

Fig. 5. Structure of developed ANN controller.

Fig. 6. Simulation block of the ANN controller.

The Simulink model of the ANN controller is shown in Figure 7. It has three layers, namely input, hidden, and output layer. The PI controller of the SSSC controller may be replaced with this ANN with the same input. The Output of the ANN V_{qref} is given to the SSSC.

Fig. 7. Internal architecture of the ANN controller.

VII. SIMULATION RESULTS

The suggested SSSC with the ANN controller was successfully simulated in MATLAB/Simulink. Under various

system conditions of a multi-machine power system, the PI controller and the ANN controller were compared and their performance was evaluated.

A. System Response without SSSC for Various Fault Transient Durations

The simulation response for a 3 phase fault at bus B3 for fault durations of 0.32 sec, 0.34 sec, and 0.4 sec are shown in Figure 8. The results indicate that as the fault duration increases, the real power variations, the variation in rotor angle, and system oscillations also increase, along with settling time and first peak.

Fig. 8. System without SSSC. Various fault durations. (a) Real power control, (b) rotor angle response.

B. System Response with PI-based SSSC

1) System Response for Various Fault Transient Durations

Figure 9 shows the plot for power flow in MW and the rotor angle with a PI controller having two input variables. For comparison, a 3 Φ fault is generated between B2 and B3 bus for various transient durations of 0.32 sec, 0.322 sec and 0.323 sec using the three phase fault generator. PI control is used to suppress the rotor angle δ during fault conditions. The system's transient stability is maintained by the PI-based SSSC. The inter area oscillations caused by the three-phase fault are shown in Figure 9(c). The findings show that using the PI-based SSSC, the speed deviation difference is quite minor. The response indicates that the oscillations increased with increase in fault duration.

2) System Response for Various Load Conditions

System response with various load conditions at the receiving end is shown in Figure 10. From the result, it can be concluded that the line power is more for 6000 MW load as compared to 6800 MW load.

Fig. 9. PI SSSC. Various fault transient durations. (a) Real power control, (b) rotor angle response, (c) speed deviation (W1-W2) rad/sec.

Fig. 10. PI SSSC. Various load conditions. (a) Real power control, (b) rotor angle response, (c) speed deviation (W1-W2) rad/sec.

Fig. 11. ANN SSSC. Various fault transient durations. (a) Real power control, (b) rotor angle response, (c) speed deviation (W1-W2) rad/sec.

Fig. 12. ANN SSSC. Various load conditions. (a) Real power control, (b) rotor angle response, (c) speed deviation (W1-W2) rad/sec.

C. System Response with the ANN-based SSSC

1) System Response for Various Fault Transient Durations

The simulation results of the system with the ANN-based SSSC are shown in Figure 11.

2) System Response at Various Load Conditions

Under various load conditions, the results of the SSSC with ANN for a three phase fault of 0.22 sec duration are shown in Figure 12. The results show that the system is more stable for 5000 MW applied load. The difference in system performance parameters at 7000 MW and 8000 MW applied load is quite minor.

D. ANN-PI Control System Response Comparison

1) Power Flow

Figure 13 illustrates the comparative response of PI and ANN controller line power with respect to time, with a fault introduced between buses B2 and B3 for duration 0.22 sec. We can draw the conclusion that the ANN control of the SSSC enhances power flow. Compared with the PI control, the actual power improves by over 10% with ANN control.

Fig. 13. Damping response. Red: ANN controller, Blue: PI controller.

2) Rotor Angle Response

The deviation graph of the rotor angle with PI controlled and ANN controlled SSSC with fault induced for a duration of 0.22 sec is shown in Figure 14. The rotor angle is decreased by ANN control during fault conditions.

Fig. 14. Rotor angle variation. Red: ANN controller, Blue: PI controller.

3) Speed Deviation

The simulation's output, given in Figure 15, depicts the inter-area oscillations ($\Delta w1 - \Delta w2$), that occur during a three-phase failure at the receiving end between buses B2 and B3. The findings show that when compared to PI controller, the suggested ANN controller performs better dynamically and damps quicker the oscillations under abnormal conditions.

Fig. 15. Speed deviation. Red: ANN controller, Blue: PI controller.

VIII. DISCUSSION

The comparative response of the PI and ANN controllers displayed line power against time, with a fault caused between buses B2 and B3 for duration 0.22 sec. The ANN control of the SSSC improves power flow. In comparison to PI control, the ANN control enhances real power by more than 10%. Considering the inter-area oscillations ($\Delta w1 - \Delta w2$), the findings show that the suggested ANN controlled SSSC outperforms the PI controller. The simulation result summary with respect to rotor angle, indicating the increased damping performance of the designed ANN controller over the PI based-controller is shown in Table I.

TABLE I. COMPARATIVE PERFORMANCE OF ANN BASED SSSC AND PI BASED SSSC WITH RESPECT TO ROTOR ANGLE

Controller	First peak for 0.22 sec fault duration	Settling time of response	No. of oscillations
PI based	136 deg	8.3 sec	4
ANN based	108 deg	8 sec	3

Table I indicates that the ANN-based SSSC significantly improved the damping performance during sudden large disturbance, thus improving power system security.

IX. CONCLUSION

As the performance of the PI-based SSSC degrades with changing system conditions, an intelligent controller for SSSC is necessary. There are very few articles that discuss ANN-based SSSC. The current research describes the standard PI-based SSSC performance in both steady-state and abnormal conditions. For damping oscillations under fault conditions, an ANN-based SSSC is constructed with two input variables: voltage change and voltage rate of change. The local mode of oscillations is investigated. The multimachine model of the sample system is used to validate the function of the proposed SSSC controller in MATLAB. The ANN and PI controller designs for the system's SSSC are presented. Under various system conditions, comparative performance of the controllers is shown in terms of the line's ability to handle power, rotor angle deviation, bus voltage, terminal voltage, and inter-area oscillations. The proposed ANN controller provides higher dynamic performance when compared to the PI controller. The findings demonstrate that, in contrast to the PI controller, the use of ANN-based control in abnormal conditions immediately damps power oscillations and improves power flow.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. N. Dhurvey and V. K. Chandrakar, "Improvement of Power System Performance Using Fuzzy Logic Based Interline Power Flow Controller [IPFC]," *Journal of Power and Energy Engineering*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 67–77, Apr. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.4236/jpee.2016.44007>.
- [2] V. K. Chandrakar and A. G. Kothari, "Fuzzy-based Static Synchronous Compensator (STATCOM) for improving transient stability performance," *International Journal of Energy Technology and Policy*, vol. 5, no. 6, pp. 692–707, Jan. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJETP.2007.015623>.
- [3] L. L. Sonfack, G. Kenné, and A. M. Fombu, "A New Static Synchronous Series Compensator Control Strategy Based on RBF Neuro-Sliding Mode Technique for Power Flow Control and DC Voltage Regulation," *Electric Power Components and Systems*, vol. 46, no. 4, pp. 456–471, Feb. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1080/15325008.2018.1445795>.
- [4] M. V. U. Maheswari and P. Mahesh, "Compare The effectiveness of SSSC in Transmission network using PI and ANN control with POD Controller," *International Journal for Modern Trends in Science and Technology*, vol. 8, no. 9, pp. 213–236, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.46501/IJMTST0809047>.
- [5] V. K. Chandrakar and A. G. Kothari, "Comparison of RBFN and fuzzy based STATCOM controllers for transient stability improvement," in *2007 International Aegean Conference on Electrical Machines and Power Electronics*, 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACEMP.2007.4510556>.
- [6] V. K. Chandrakar and A. G. Kothari, "MFFN based Static Synchronous Series Compensator (SSSC) for Transient Stability improvement," in *2007 International Conference on Intelligent Systems Applications to Power Systems*, Kaohsiung, Taiwan, 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISAP.2007.4441647>.
- [7] S. Chandrakar, J. Helonde, R. M. Mohril, and V. K. Chandrakar, "Fuzzy based SVC with coordinated POD for damping of oscillations of power system," *WSEAS Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 253–262, Jan. 2010.
- [8] V. K. Chandrakar and A. G. Kothari, "Fuzzy logic based static synchronous series compensator (SSSC) for transient stability improvement," in *2004 IEEE International Conference on Electric Utility Deregulation, Restructuring and Power Technologies. Proceedings*, 2004, <https://doi.org/10.1109/DRPT.2004.1338500>.
- [9] V. P. Rajderkar and V. K. Chandrakar, "Design Coordination of a Fuzzy-based Unified Power Flow Controller with Hybrid Energy Storage for Enriching Power System Dynamics," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 10027–10032, Feb. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5508>.
- [10] V. K. Chandrakar and A. G. Kothari, "RBFN based Static Synchronous Series Compensator (SSSC) for Transient Stability improvement," in *2006 9th International Conference on Control, Automation, Robotics and Vision*, Singapore, 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICARCV.2006.345227>.
- [11] P. Vaidya and V. K. Chandrakar, "Exploring the Enhanced Performance of a Static Synchronous Compensator with a Super-Capacitor in Power Networks," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 9703–9708, Dec. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5317>.
- [12] H. F. Wang, "Design of SSSC damping controller to improve power system oscillation stability," in *1999 IEEE Africon. 5th Africon Conference in Africa (Cat. No.99CH36342)*, Cape Town, South Africa, 1999, <https://doi.org/10.1109/AFRCON.1999.820931>.
- [13] K. K. Sen, "SSSC-static synchronous series compensator: theory, modeling, and application," *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 241–246, 1998, <https://doi.org/10.1109/61.660884>.
- [14] S. Amara and H. A. Hsan, "Power system stability improvement by FACTS devices: A comparison between STATCOM, SSSC and UPFC," in *2012 First International Conference on Renewable Energies and Vehicular Technology*, Nabeul, Tunisia, 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1109/REVET.2012.6195297>.
- [15] K. Padma and K. Vaisakh, "Application of AHP method for optimal location of SSSC device under different operating conditions," in *2016 International Conference on Intelligent Control Power and Instrumentation (ICICPI)*, Kolkata, India, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICICPI.2016.7859704>.
- [16] Y. I. Lal and B. Satyadharma, "Stability Enhancement for Transmission Lines using Neural Network in Static Synchronous Series Compensator," *International Journal of Scientific Engineering and Technology*, vol. 4, no. 6, pp. 365–369, 2015.

Enhanced Sea Horse Optimization with Deep Learning-based Multimodal Fusion Technique for Rice Plant Disease Segmentation and Classification

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ABSTRACT

The detection of diseases in rice plants is an essential step in ensuring healthy crop growth and maximizing yields. A real-time and accurate plant disease detection technique can assist in the development of mitigation strategies to ensure food security on a large scale and economical rice crop protection. An accurate classification of rice plant diseases using DL and computer vision could create a foundation to achieve a site-specific application of agrochemicals. Image investigation tools are efficient for the early diagnosis of plant diseases and the continuous monitoring of plant health status. This article presents an Enhanced Sea Horse Optimization with Deep Learning-based Multimodal Fusion for Rice Plant Disease Detection and Classification (ESHODL-MFRPDC) technique. The proposed technique employed a DL-based fusion process with a hyperparameter tuning strategy to achieve an improved rice plant disease detection performance. The ESHODL-MFRPDC approach used Bilateral Filtering (BF)-based noise removal and contrast enhancement as a preprocessing step. Furthermore, Mayfly Optimization (MFO) with a Multi-Level Thresholding (MLT) based segmentation process was used to recognize the diseased portions in the leaf image. A fusion of three DL models was used for feature extraction, namely Residual Network (ResNet50), Xception, and NASNet. The Quasi-Recurrent Neural Network (QRNN) was used for the recognition of rice plant diseases, and its hyperparameters were set using the ESHO method. The performance of the ESHODL-MFRPDC method was validated using the rice leaf disease dataset from the UCI database. An extensive comparison study demonstrated the promising performance of the proposed method over others.

Keywords-agriculture; plant disease detection; rice crops; computer vision; deep learning; sea horse optimizer

I. INTRODUCTION

Rice is an essential food in several nations around the world. Approximately half the world's population depends on rice-based food, while the world population will exceed nine billion in 2050. As rice plant diseases reduce production by 10-15%, it is a great challenge to ensure food protection for massive amounts of the population and the agricultural society [1]. Bacteria and fungi are the main causes of these diseases, which result in a decrease in rice production and an increase in the economic expenses of farmers [2]. Therefore, the detection of diseases in agricultural goods in their initial stages is crucial to prevent production loss and improve quality. Traditionally, the detection of diseases in rice plants can be performed by culturing pathogens in the laboratory or based on a visual

assessment of symptoms. Visual evaluation is subjective and prone to inaccuracy [3]. Culturing pathogens in the lab is a time-consuming procedure and there is no guarantee of achieving results in time. These traditional techniques require specialists for the identification of diseases, and it is complicated for farmers to access them [4]. These problems have encouraged the research communities to examine different methods for developing automated classification and identification techniques for diseases of rice plants [5].

A computer vision approach can be used to identify plant diseases and can be a valuable tool to manage disease and breeding resistance [6]. Recently, pattern detection approaches and image processing have been used for the diagnosis of plant diseases. The quality of agriculture and its products could also

be evaluated using images and various methods based on Artificial Intelligence (AI) [7]. The application of computer vision and AI to automatically detect and identify rice plant diseases is currently being widely studied, as manual supervision of plant diseases is uninteresting, time-consuming, and laborious [8]. Today, Deep Learning (DL) methods are very often applied in the diagnosis of diseases. However, due to the need for higher hardware resources to train Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) in many large databases, it takes a long time and is not favorable to its advancement and usage [9]. Authors in [10] suggest a Transfer Learning (TL) method to identify the combination of pre-trained processes using databases of diseased rice plant leaves to train the system.

This paper presents an Enhanced Sea Horse Optimization with Deep Learning-based Multimodal Fusion technique for Rice Plant Disease Detection and Classification (ESHODL-MFRPDC). This approach uses a DL-based fusion process with hyperparameter tuning to improve rice plant disease detection performance. The ESHODL-MFRPDC approach uses Bilateral Filtering (BF)-based noise removal and contrast enhancement as a preprocessing step. Then, Mayfly Optimization (MFO) with a Multi-Level Thresholding (MLT)-based segmentation process is used to recognize the diseased portions in the leaf image. A fusion of three DL models is used for feature extraction, namely Residual Network (ResNet50), Xception, and NASNet. The Quasi-Recurrent Neural Network (QRNN) model is used for the recognition of rice plant disease, and its hyperparameters can be altered using the ESHO method. The performance of the ESHODL-MFRPDC method was validated in the UCI rice leaf disease dataset and compared with other methods.

II. RELATED WORKS

In [11], an automated recognition system using CNN was proposed to detect rice leaf diseases, but its accuracy is highly questionable. In [12], a novel DL-based Automated Plant Disease Detection and Classification (DLAPDDC) approach was proposed, in which U2Net-based context elimination was used to extract leaf and fruit areas, SqueezeNet with Adam optimization was used for feature extraction, and finally, the XGBoost approach was used to classify plant diseases. In [13], preprocessed input images of various rice plant diseases were detected using GLCM and ANNs. This approach is extremely useful for farmers to detect rice diseases early and stop the use of pesticides that affect crop production. In [14], the ADSNN-BO approach was presented, based on MobileNet design and the augmented attention process, using the Bayesian Optimizer (BO) to tune its hyperparameters. This method was cross-validated on an open disease database with 4 types in total. To verify its interpretability, the system used an activation map and a filter visualization system. In [15], a system was proposed to present visual data to agriculturalists and allow them to decide on the necessary defensive processes. A lightweight DL system, based on the Vision Transformer (ViT) and a CNN, was presented for real-time automated plant disease classification. In [16], a real-time approach using DCNN was proposed to detect corn leaf diseases. DNN performance was improved by tuning the hyperparameters and modifying the pooling combination on a GPU system.

Moreover, the parameter count of the established system was optimized to make it appropriate for real-time application. The pre-training DCNN approach can be used on a Raspberry Pi 3, using Intel Movidius Neural. In [17], an EfficientNet DL was proposed for the classification of plant leaf diseases. EfficientNet and other DL approaches were trained to use a Transfer Learning (TL) system. During the TL method, every layer of the method was fixed and trainable.

III. THE PROPOSED MODEL

This study presents an automatic rice plant disease recognition and classification technique using a DL-based fusion process with a hyperparameter tuning strategy to achieve improved rice plant disease detection performance. The proposed model consists of image preprocessing, MFO with MLT-based segmentation, QRNN and fusion-based classification and extraction, and ESHO-based hyperparameter tuning. Initially, the input plant leaf images are preprocessed to improve their quality. Then, the diseased portions are accurately segmented by the MFO with MLT. Afterward, the fusion process is carried out to generate a set of feature vectors. Lastly, the ESHO with QRNN is used for the disease detection and classification procedure. Figure 1 shows the complete workflow of the ESHODL-MFRPDC method.

Fig. 1. The overall flow of the ESHODL-MFRPDC method.

A. Image Preprocessing

BF-based noise removal and contrast enhancement were used to preprocess the images. BF is a non-linear smoothing approach that aims to maintain edges and significant structural data of the image but decrease noise [18]. It assumes both spatial and intensity variances among neighboring pixels in the filter method. The BF system computes a weighted average of the pixel values in the well-defined neighborhood, but the weight can be resolved by the spatial distance and intensity

similarity between the center pixel and its neighbors. Smoothing counts and edge preservation are controlled by altering the filter parameters, such as intensity and spatial kernels. Then, CLAHE was employed to enhance the local contrast of the image by redistributing the intensity values from its histogram. CLAHE splits the image at lesser areas, termed tiles, and executes Histogram Equalization (HE) individually to all tiles. The "contrast limited" feature of CLAHE avoids excessive noise amplification by clipping the histogram later to a certain limit. It confirms that the contrast enhancement was restricted, averting artifacts and maintaining the entire image's qualities.

B. MFO with MLT-based Segmentation

Once the input images are preprocessed, the segmentation process is performed by the MFO using the MLT approach. MFO is a population-based method consisting of the following succeeding functions: (i) initializes an equivalent amount of male and female agents, (ii) allows male Mayflies (MFs) to identify the best location as *loc* for the preferred task, (iii) allows the female MF to search and fuse with a male MF placed at *loc*, (iv) generate an offspring, and (v) end the search and display the concluding output. In [19], a threshold-based technique was presented to calculate the optimal threshold for the segmentation and increasing entropy. An objective function was obtained for the computation of the bi-level threshold:

$$FUN_{kap}(t) = k_1 + k_2 \quad (1)$$

where k_1 and k_2 are calculated as:

$$k_1 = \sum_{s=1}^t \frac{p_s}{\omega_0} \ln \left(\frac{p_s}{\omega_0} \right) \quad (2)$$

$$k_2 = \sum_{s=(t+1)}^L \frac{p_s}{\omega_1} \ln \left(\frac{p_s}{\omega_1} \right) \quad (3)$$

where p_s denotes the probability distribution of the intensity level of the grayscales, and ω_0 and ω_1 indicate the probability distribution for k_1 and k_2 class labels. This entropy-based method is as flexible as possible for MLT. Therefore, there is a need to divide the images into n -class labels using the $(n-1)$ threshold number.

$$FUN_{kap}(T) = \sum_{s=1}^n k_s \quad (4)$$

$T = [t_1, t_2, t(n-1)]$ represents a vector consisting of a threshold number. The entropy is defined separately with the corresponding threshold t value and the following equation was adapted for n entropy:

$$k_n^c = \sum_{i=t(n+1)}^L \frac{p_i}{\omega_{(n-1)}} \ln \left(\frac{p_i}{\omega_{(n-1)}} \right) \quad (5)$$

where $(\omega_0, \omega_1, \dots, \omega_{(n-1)})$ represents the probability of occurrence for n classes, and the MFO technique is used for the optimal threshold number. Similarly, the MFO method was projected for the mating process and the fighting feature of MFs [20]. The MFs in swarms can be identified as male and female individuals. The MFO method changes the location based on the velocity $velocity_i(t)$ and location $loc_i(t)$ at the existing iteration:

$$loc_i(time + 1) = loc_i(time) + velocity_i(time + 1) \quad (6)$$

Each male and female MF changes location using (6) about time, but it can be applied to velocity-adapting features. The half-male and female MFs pass over mating and produce children. The offspring were produced in the parent as follows:

$$offspr_1 = PxMale + (1 - P)xFemale \quad (7)$$

$$offspr_2 = PxFemale + (1 - P)xMale \quad (8)$$

where P denotes a Gauss distribution random number.

C. Fusion-based Feature Extraction

In this phase, fusion-based feature extraction was carried out using three DL models, namely ResNet50 [21], Xception [22], and NASNet [23]. The resultant features were fused by the entropy approach. Entropy-based feature fusion uses the concept of entropy to combine features from multiple sources. Entropy measures the amount of information or uncertainty in a set of data. In the context of feature fusion, entropy can be used as a criterion to determine the importance or relevance of individual features.

D. Image Classification using the QRNN Model

In the final stage, the QRNN model receives the features to classify them. QRNN is an NN fusion of CNNs and LSTMs, integrating the merits of both [24]. QRNNs are extremely parallelizable like CNNs. All QRNN layers integrate 2 seed mechanisms related to the convolution and pooling layers in CNNs. The formulas for the QRNN unit are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{x}_t &= \tanh(W \times X_t) \\ f_t &= \sigma(W_f \times X_t) \\ o_t &= \sigma(W_o \times X_t) \\ c_t &= f_t \odot c_{t-1} + (1 - f_t) \odot \hat{x}_t \\ h_t &= o_t \odot \tanh(c_t) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $X_t \in \mathbb{R}^{k \times n}$ implies the input series of k n -dimensional vectors $x_{t-(k+1)}, \dots, x_t$ and mask convolutional beside the timestep size. W, W_f and W_o are all convolution filter banks in $\mathbb{R}^{d \times n \times k}$, and k denotes the filter width. The three primary terms are QRNN convolution segments that can create m -dimension series \hat{x}_t, f_t , and o_t . The symbol \odot signifies element-wise multiplication. The final 2 terms are pooling parts of QRNN, while the familiar element-wise gates perform in the LSTM unit. As shown in (9), a single QRNN performs three multivector functions that depend on the input sequence X , without dependency on prior outcomes as $h_{(t-1)}$. With known input, these multiply-vector functions $W \times X_t$ are pre-calculated in several time steps. Thus, weighted matrices with a huge count of memory do not require to be loaded at every time step. Therefore, these functions are correlated in a single matrix to matrix multiplication, as shown in (10):

$$u^T = \begin{pmatrix} W \\ W_f \\ W_o \end{pmatrix} [X_{(k-1)}, X_k, \dots, X_{L+(k-1)}] \quad (10)$$

where $U \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times 3d}$, d , and $L = T - (k + 1)$ refer to the combined outcome matrix, hidden state neuron count, and the length of the input sequence.

E. Hyperparameter Tuning using the ESHO Algorithm

The Enhanced Sea Horse Optimization (ESHO) technique was used to improve the accuracy of the QRNN approach. Sea Horse Optimization (SHO) is motivated by the breeding, natural displacement, and predation strategies of Sea Horses (SHs) [25]. This technique has three major elements: mobility predation, and breeding. Global and local search models were introduced for the social behavior of predation and mobility, similarly to equalizing the exploration and exploitation of the method. The SHO can be split into four stages: initialization, mobility, predation, and breeding behaviors of SHs. SHO, like other metaheuristics, begins with the initial population. Once a SH signifies a feasible solution to the issue from the searching space, the entire populace of SHs is represented as:

$$S = \begin{bmatrix} x_1^1 & \dots & x_1^D \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_P^1 & \dots & x_P^D \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

where P , s , D , and UB and LB indicate the population size, seahorses, variable's dimension, and the Upper and Lower Bounds of the problems, respectively, that are used as starting points for the randomly generated solution. In the search space, for the i^{th} individual's X_i :

$$X_i = [x_i^1, \dots, x_i^D] \quad (12)$$

$$x_i^j = rand \times (UB^j - LB^j) + LB^j \quad (13)$$

where $rand$ denotes a random value in the interval [0,1], x_i^j signifies the j^{th} variable in the i^{th} individual, i refers to the integer with a positive value in the interval [1, P], and j represents an integer with positive values within [1, D]. The optimized upper and lower boundaries of the j^{th} parameter of the optimized problems is indicated as LB^j and UB^j . The fittest individual is designated by X_{best} using the maximal or minimal optimization tasks and is considered the lowest or highest fitness level.

$$X_{best} = arg_{\min \text{ or } \max} (f(X)) \quad (14)$$

In (14), $f(X_i)$ shows the objective function value for certain tasks. During movement, the movement pattern of SHs corresponds to the uniformly distributed random value within [0, 1]. Now, set $r_1 = 0$ as a cut-off point to tradeoff between the performance of exploration and exploitation, with half going to the global search and the rest to local mining. The ESHO method grows a Fitness Function (FF) to obtain an optimal classifier solution. This gives a positive integer to signify the optimum solution of candidate performances. In such cases, the reduction of the classifier error rate can be assumed to be as follows:

$$fitness(x_i) = \frac{ClassifierErrorRate(x_i) = \frac{\text{no.of misclassified instances}}{\text{Total no.of instances}} \times 100}{1} \quad (15)$$

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The effectiveness of the ESHODL-MFRPDC technique was investigated in a plant disease dataset [27-28], consisting of 215 instances with 5 classes. Table I shows the experimental leaf disease recognition results of the ESHODL-MFRPDC

approach, using a 70:30 for TRP/TSP, offering $accu_y$, $prec_n$, $sens_y$, $spec_y$, and F_{score} of 98%, 94.74%, 97.30%, 98.23%, and 96%, respectively. The simulation was performed using Python 3.6.5 on an i5-8600K, 250GB SSD, GeForce 1050Ti 4GB, 16GB RAM, and 1TB HDD PC. The parameter settings were learning rate: 0.01, activation: ReLU, epoch count: 50, dropout: 0.5, and batch size: 5. Figure 2 shows a comparison of ESHODL-MFRPDC with other DL methods [29]. The results show that the DAE and ANN methods performed worse, DNN, SIFT-SVM, and SIFT-KNN performed better, and DNN-JOA and CNN provided even better results. The ESHODL-MFRPDC method achieved maximum performance with $accu_y$ of 98.77%, $prec_n$ of 97.21%, $sens_y$ of 97.65%, $spec_y$ of 99.22%, and F_{score} of 97.30%.

TABLE I. LEAF DISEASE RECOGNITION RESULTS OF ESHODL-MFRPDC ON 70:30 OF TRP/TSP

Class	Accu _y	Prec _n	Sens _y	Spec _y	F _{score}
Training Phase (70%)					
Bacterial Leaf Blight	99.33	100.00	95.65	100.00	97.78
Brown Spot	99.33	100.00	96.00	100.00	97.96
Leaf Smut	98.67	100.00	93.33	100.00	96.55
Leaf Scaled	98.00	92.11	100.00	97.39	95.89
Rice Blast	98.00	94.74	97.30	98.23	96.00
Average	98.67	97.37	96.46	99.12	96.84
Testing Phase (30%)					
Bacterial Leaf Blight	96.92	100.00	88.24	100.00	93.75
Brown Spot	98.46	92.31	100.00	98.11	96.00
Leaf Smut	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
Leaf Scaled	98.46	93.75	100.00	98.00	96.77
Rice Blast	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
Average	98.77	97.21	97.65	99.22	97.30

Fig. 2. Comparison of ESHODL-MFRPDC results with other DL algorithms.

Figure 3 shows a Computation Time (CT) test of the ESHODL-MFRPDC. The results identify the effectual efficiency of the ESHODL-MFRPDC model with a minimal CT of 0.12s. In contrast, the DNN-JOA, DNN, DAE, ANN, CNN, SIFT-SVM, and SIFT-KNN models reached at maximum CT of 0.29 s, 0.26 s, 0.27 s, 0.25 s, 0.25 s, 0.29 s and 0.27 s, respectively. These results highlight the greater efficiency of ESHODL-MFRPDC over the other models.

Fig. 3. CT results of ESHODL-MFRPDC approach with other DL methods.

V. CONCLUSION

This study presented an automatic rice plant disease recognition and classification technique. The proposed ESHODL-MFRPDC method uses a DL-based fusion process with a hyperparameter tuning strategy to improve rice plant disease detection performance. This method consists of image preprocessing, MFO with MLT-based segmentation, QRNN and fusion-based classification and extraction, and ESHO-based hyperparameter tuning. The ESHO model aids in the optimal choice of the hyperparameters of the QRNN model, resulting in improved classification performance. The effectiveness of the ESHODL-MFRPDC technique was validated on a rice leaf disease dataset from the UCI database. An extensive comparison of the results with other methods demonstrated the effectiveness of the proposed ESHODL-MFRPDC technique in both performance and computation time.

REFERENCES

- [1] V. Tiwari, R. C. Joshi, and M. K. Dutta, "Dense convolutional neural networks based multiclass plant disease detection and classification using leaf images," *Ecological Informatics*, vol. 63, Jul. 2021, Art. no. 101289, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoinf.2021.101289>.
- [2] V. K. Shrivastava, M. K. Pradhan, S. Minz, and M. P. Thakur, "Rice Plant Disease Classification Using Transfer Learning of Deep Convolution Network," in *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, New Delhi, India, Jul. 2019, vol. XLII-3/W6, pp. 631–635, <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLII-3-W6-631-2019>.
- [3] N. P. S. Rathore and D. L. Prasad, "Automatic Rice Plant Disease Recognition and Identification Using Convolutional Neural Network," *Journal of Critical Reviews*, vol. 7, no. 15, 2020.
- [4] A. M., M. Zekiwo, and A. Bruck, "Deep Learning-Based Image Processing for Cotton Leaf Disease and Pest Diagnosis," *Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 2021, Jun. 2021, Art. no. e9981437, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/9981437>.
- [5] Md. J. Hasan, S. Mahub, Md. S. Alom, and Md. Abu Nasim, "Rice Disease Identification and Classification by Integrating Support Vector Machine With Deep Convolutional Neural Network," in *2019 1st International Conference on Advances in Science, Engineering and Robotics Technology (ICASERT)*, Dhaka, Bangladesh, Feb. 2019, pp. 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICASERT.2019.8934568>.
- [6] V. K. Shrivastava, M. K. Pradhan, and M. P. Thakur, "Application of Pre-Trained Deep Convolutional Neural Networks for Rice Plant Disease Classification," in *2021 International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Smart Systems (ICAIS)*, Coimbatore, India, Mar. 2021, pp. 1023–1030, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICAIS50930.2021.9395813>.
- [7] N. Senan, M. Aamir, R. Ibrahim, N. S., and W. H. N. Wan, "An Efficient Convolutional Neural Network for Paddy Leaf Disease and Pest Classification," *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, vol. 11, no. 7, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.14569/IJACSA.2020.0110716>.
- [8] S. Sundaralingam and N. Ramanathan, "A Deep Learning-Based approach to Segregate Solid Waste Generated in Residential Areas," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 10439–10446, Apr. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5716>.
- [9] K. Rajeshkumar, C. Ananth, and N. Mohananthini, "Blockchain-Assisted Homomorphic Encryption Approach for Skin Lesion Diagnosis using Optimal Deep Learning Model," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 10978–10983, Jun. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5594>.
- [10] D. Elangovan and V. Subedha, "Adaptive Particle Grey Wolf Optimizer with Deep Learning-based Sentiment Analysis on Online Product Reviews," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 10989–10993, Jun. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5787>.
- [11] Md. A. Islam, Md. Nymur, M. Shamsoddin, S. Hasan, Md. Shahadat, and T. Khatun, "An Automated Convolutional Neural Network Based Approach for Paddy Leaf Disease Detection," *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, vol. 12, no. 1, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.14569/IJACSA.2021.0120134>.
- [12] A. Pavithra, G. Kalpana, and T. Vigneswaran, "Deep learning-based automated disease detection and classification model for precision agriculture," *Soft Computing*, Mar. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00500-023-07936-0>.
- [13] U. Kiruthika, R. S. Kanagasuba, R. Jaichandran, and C. Priyadarshini, "Detection and Classification of Paddy Crop Disease using Deep Learning Techniques," *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 4353–4359, Sep. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.35940/ijrte.C5506.098319>.
- [14] Y. Wang, H. Wang, and Z. Peng, "Rice diseases detection and classification using attention based neural network and bayesian optimization," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 178, Sep. 2021, Art. no. 114770, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2021.114770>.
- [15] Y. Borhani, J. Khoramdel, and E. Najafi, "A deep learning based approach for automated plant disease classification using vision transformer," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 12, no. 1, Jul. 2022, Art. no. 11554, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-15163-0>.
- [16] S. Mishra, R. Sachan, and D. Rajpal, "Deep Convolutional Neural Network based Detection System for Real-time Corn Plant Disease Recognition," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 167, pp. 2003–2010, Jan. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2020.03.236>.
- [17] Ü. Atila, M. Uçar, K. Akyol, and E. Uçar, "Plant leaf disease classification using EfficientNet deep learning model," *Ecological Informatics*, vol. 61, Mar. 2021, Art. no. 101182, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoinf.2020.101182>.
- [18] B. Desai, U. Kushwaha, and S. Jha, "Image Filtering - Techniques, Algorithm and Applications," *GIS Science Journal*, vol. 7, no. 11, pp. 970–975, 2020.
- [19] J. N. Kapur, P. K. Sahoo, and A. K. C. Wong, "A new method for gray-level picture thresholding using the entropy of the histogram," *Computer Vision, Graphics, and Image Processing*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 273–285, Mar. 1985, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0734-189X\(85\)90125-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0734-189X(85)90125-2).
- [20] R. Mahum, M. Sharaf, H. Hassan, L. Liang, and B. Huang, "A Robust Brain Tumor Detector Using BiLSTM and Mayfly Optimization and Multi-Level Thresholding," *Biomedicines*, vol. 11, no. 6, Jun. 2023, Art. no. 1715, <https://doi.org/10.3390/biomedicines11061715>.
- [21] M. T. Aziz *et al.*, "A Novel Hybrid Approach for Classifying Osteosarcoma Using Deep Feature Extraction and Multilayer Perceptron," *Diagnostics*, vol. 13, no. 12, Jan. 2023, Art. no. 2106, <https://doi.org/10.3390/diagnostics13122106>.

- [22] S. Swati, M. Sharma, and L. Vig, "Automatic Classification of Low-Resolution Chromosomal Images," in *Computer Vision – ECCV 2018 Workshops*, Munich, Germany, 2019, pp. 315–325, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-11024-6_21.
- [23] M. K. Dahouda and I. Joe, "Neural Architecture Search Net-Based Feature Extraction With Modular Neural Network for Image Classification of Copper/ Cobalt Raw Minerals," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 72253–72262, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3187420>.
- [24] C. Yang, W. Wang, X. Zhang, Q. Guo, T. Zhu, and Q. Ai, "A Parallel Electrical Optimized Load Forecasting Method Based on Quasi-Recurrent Neural Network," *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, vol. 696, no. 1, Nov. 2021, Art. no. 012040, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/696/1/012040>.
- [25] F. A. Özbay, "A modified seahorse optimization algorithm based on chaotic maps for solving global optimization and engineering problems," *Engineering Science and Technology, an International Journal*, vol. 41, May 2023, Art. no. 101408, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jestch.2023.101408>.
- [26] H. Alahmer *et al.*, "Optimal Water Addition in Emulsion Diesel Fuel Using Machine Learning and Sea-Horse Optimizer to Minimize Exhaust Pollutants from Diesel Engine," *Atmosphere*, vol. 14, no. 3, Mar. 2023, Art. no. 449, <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos14030449>.
- [27] H. B. Prajapati, J. P. Shah, and V. K. Dabhi, "Detection and classification of rice plant diseases," *Intelligent Decision Technologies*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 357–373, Jan. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.3233/IDT-170301>.
- [28] M. F. Hossain, "Dhan-Shomadhan: A Dataset of Rice Leaf Disease Classification for Bangladeshi Local Rice." arXiv, Sep. 14, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2309.07515>.
- [29] R. P. Narmadha, N. Sengottaiyan, and R. J. Kavitha, "Deep Transfer Learning Based Rice Plant Disease Detection Model," *Intelligent Automation & Soft Computing*, vol. 31, no. 2, pp. 1257–1271, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.32604/iasc.2022.020679>.

The Influence of UHPFRC Jacket Steel Fiber Content on Strengthening Damaged Columns

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ABSTRACT

Steel fiber is a commonly used material to repair damaged concrete, caused by environmental or design issues. This study used various Micro-copper-coated Steel Fiber (MSF) content (0.0, 0.5, 2.0, and 2.5%) with varying aspect ratios (28, 37, and 45) as part of Ultra-High-Performance Fiber-Reinforced Concrete (UHPFRC) mixtures to repair damaged concrete columns using a 30 mm layer jacketing. Twelve columns were prepared and tested at first by loading them with roughly 90% of their ultimate axial load capacity. Damage was caused and the columns were subsequently strengthened and rebuilt using UHPFRC mixtures in 30-mm layer jacketing for a second test, to determine the effect of UHPFRC and MSF content on damaged and reinforced columns. The test results showed that the concrete properties improved as the MSF content increased to 2.0% of the volume fraction, beyond which there was a slight reduction. Additionally, the UHPFRC-strengthened columns with and without MSFs experienced higher load capacities than the corresponding unstrengthened. On the contrary, using 2.5% MSF in the UHPFRC decreased the loading capacity by 14% compared to the UHPFRC with 2.0% MSF. The strengthened column with 2.0% MSF content showed the highest load efficiency (165.7% compared to unstrengthened), along with substantial displacement and ductility.

Keywords-aspect ratios; UHPFRC; load capacity; MSFs; jacketing

I. INTRODUCTION

Concrete is a widely used material in various sectors of the global construction industry. With its long-term durability, concrete structures can maintain their performance levels for several decades, provided they meet the safety requirements of the construction standards. However, Reinforced Concrete (RC) constructions are vulnerable to damage due to human design errors or environmental conditions such as fires, corrosion, and natural disasters [1]. Additionally, unintentional design flaws or alterations in buildings are considered the primary contributors to structural damage to beams, columns, and slabs, compromising their ability to support dead and live loads [1-2]. Among these components, columns are singularly responsible for bearing the entire vertical load to the soil. They are among the most crucial structural components and are frequently utilized in residential and high-rise buildings. Severe overload can cause significant column damage, causing deformation of the steel bars and potentially resulting in a surface fracture that could lead to a partial or complete structural collapse. Fractures on the concrete surface also expose vulnerable areas to corrosive agents, such as salt water and high humidity, which can penetrate and reach the steel reinforcement, ultimately leading to corrosion and reducing the load-bearing capacity of the concrete, leading to structural instability over time [3].

Ensuring a proper transfer of loads to the soil is crucial, making the repair and renovation of damaged building columns

essential [4]. Repairing and reusing damaged concrete structures is often more cost-effective than demolishing and constructing new ones, although repairs can sometimes incur higher costs than new construction. However, while rehabilitation is a better alternative to demolition, it is considered one of the most challenging aspects of construction due to its inherent risks [5]. Before starting design and repair work, thorough examinations are imperative to accurately assess the condition to determine the appropriate repair materials and techniques to be used [1]. There are various solutions to rehabilitate overloaded and damaged reinforced concrete structures, with strengthening techniques being among the most commonly used for repairing damaged columns [6]. Depending on the severity of structural damage, several techniques can be applied, such as injections, removal, replacement, and jacketing.

Jacketing, in particular, finds frequent application in strengthening damaged RC columns, using three approaches: concrete jacketing, steel jacketing, and composite jacketing [2, 7]. Many studies have investigated the use of jackets made from Normal-Strength Concrete (NSC) and Ultra-High-Performance Fiber-Reinforced Self-compacting Concrete (UHPFRSC) to strengthen and repair columns. Compared to the unjacketed reference columns, the results show that both materials have better load-carrying capabilities and higher axial displacements. Moreover, RC columns can be repaired and strengthened using NSC as a jacketing material. However, UHPFRSC with steel fibers is more successful than others [1].

In [8], 37 specimens were examined at various eccentricities, ranging from $e/t = 0 - 25\%$, and were divided into three groups: Group 1 comprised control columns with 5 specimens under various eccentricities, Group 2 used different amounts of steel wire mesh to reinforce 16 columns, and Group 3 used 16 specimens strengthened using a sandwich configuration of external vertical steel bars ($3\text{Ø}8$) on the compression side along with varying layers of steel wire mesh. All groups were coated with cement mortar. The results showed that the use of wire mesh jacketing increased the load-carrying capacity by up to 23% while using a sandwich wrapping system consisting of external vertical steel bars on the compression side and steel wire mesh increased capacity by up to 54%.

Composite jacketing is a contemporary approach that uses UHPFRC to extend the service life of RC structures at an affordable cost. UHPFRC can increase bearing capacity even in the presence of concrete cracks and significantly improve the structural longevity of structural concrete [1]. UHPFRC mixtures consist of steel fiber, water, superplasticizer (SP), Silica Fume (SF), cement, and sand, which collectively provide strength and ductility. UHPFRC improves concrete qualities such as toughness, ductility, and durability due to its uniformly dispersed fibers [9]. This technology has been developed to extend the service life of damaged RC structures by applying it to damaged areas for repair and subsequent reuse in building maintenance [10]. In [11], high-performance fiber-reinforced concrete jackets with a compressive strength of 170 MPa were used to strengthen short-column RC concrete. The results indicated that enhanced durability signifies progress in the concrete industry, yielding sustainable and economically viable buildings that are resistant to all types of corrosion. In [1], 25

and 35 mm thick jacketing was used to strengthen and repair damaged columns subjected to around 90% of their ultimate axial load capacities. This experimental study was conducted in two groups: Group 1 used regular-strength concrete with a maximum aggregate size of 4.75 mm and steel reinforcement, while Group 2 used UHPFRC with steel reinforcement. Group 2 exhibited significantly higher ultimate load capacity than Group 1 and the unjacketed reference column, with ratios of approximately three and 1.86 times, respectively.

It is imperative to identify cost-effective and time-efficient repair methods by exploring innovative approaches and materials. For example, the utilization of Micro-copper-coated Steel Fibers (MSF) with varying aspect ratios as internal reinforcement for repair mixtures remains relatively unexplored. This study aims to investigate the effect of MSF content in different aspect ratios (28, 37, and 45) within different UHPFRC mixture compositions (0.0, 0.5, 2.0, and 2.5%), using a uniform jacket thickness of 30 mm to repair square RC damaged by exceeded load capacity. The columns were subjected to axial compression loads until failure. Load capacity, displacement, ductility, and failure modes were recorded, observed, and subsequently compared.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study investigated the effects of UHPFRC using MSF with a range of varying contents and aspect ratios as repair materials to strengthen and rehabilitate damaged columns subjected to overload. The columns were bonded on all four sides and jacketed with a fixed thickness of 30 mm. Figure 1 shows the framework of the experimental study.

Fig. 1. The experimental research method.

A. Materials

MSF, as shown in Figure 2, and SF, as shown in Figure 3, were obtained from Shandong Federal Fibre Co., Ltd. and Fosam Company Ltd., respectively. The MSF had various aspect ratios, with three different lengths of straight fibers (10-16 mm) and a fixed diameter of 0.35 mm, as shown in Table I. According to the supplier's datasheet, the SF had a strength of 7900 MPa and a specific gravity of 7.9. Sodium Naphthalene Sulfonate (SNF) was supplied by a local Saudi Arabian company to improve the durability and service life of concrete, by improving the strength of the mixture by 20-60% [12]. SP conplast SP430 was used with a specific gravity of 1.06 to improve the workability of the concrete mixture. All prepared concrete mixtures were cast using Type 1 Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC), featuring an initial settling time of more than 45 minutes. Columns were reinforced using steel bars with a diameter of 12 mm diameter, 460 MPa yield strength, 610 MPa ultimate strength, and Young's modulus of 200 GPa was obtained experimentally.

TABLE I. MSFS PROPERTIES

Fiber Properties	MSFs	MSFs	MSFs
Shape	Straight	Straight	Straight
Length (mm)	10	13	16
Diameter (mm)	0.35	0.35	0.35
Aspect ratio	28	37	45
Tensile strength, (MPa)	2800	2800	2800
Young modulus (GPa)	200 GPa	200 GPa	200 GPa
Specific gravity	7.9	7.9	7.9

Fig. 2. (a) MSF, (b) MSF of different lengths.

Fig. 3. Silica fume.

B. Column Preparations and Details

Twelve square column specimens were fabricated, each designed to adhere to a minimum longitudinal reinforcement ratio of 1% [13]. These columns acted as standard columns when subjected to overloading, subsequently undergoing repair

and reinforcement through UHPFRC jacketing. The columns had cross-sectional dimensions of 150×150 mm and a height of 500 mm, featuring 4Ø12 mm longitudinal steel reinforcement and 6Ø8 mm link bars spaced at 75 mm center-to-center, as shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Reinforcement column details.

C. Mix Design for Columns

The concrete mixes consisted of 745 kg/m³ sand, 805 kg/m³ coarse aggregates (size 10-14 mm), 250 kg/m³ water, and 550 kg/m³ OPC [14]. The concrete mixture featured sand with a relative density of 3.15, a fineness modulus of 3.4, and an absorption rate of 1%. It also incorporated natural crushed coarse aggregate with a maximum size of 14 mm and Type 1 OPC. The mix proportion was formulated to achieve a target compressive strength of 30 MPa in 28 days [13]. The mixes were used to cast columns, cubes, and dogbone specimens. The 12 square columns, along with 100 mm cube edges and dogbone samples, were cured in water for 28 days and subsequently exposed to room temperature until testing.

D. Test Setup and Column Instrumentation before Repair

Axial compression loads were applied to the columns using a hydraulic Universal Testing Machine (UTM) with a capacity of 200 tons. Steel plates were affixed to the upper and lower surfaces of each column to evenly distribute the axial load across the column. Before testing, the top surface was polished using a Gipson layer. A total of 12 RC columns were subjected to concentric axial compression loads at approximately 90% of their actual axial capacities, as shown in Figure 5, with a displacement rate of 0.5 mm/min until hairline cracks emerged, without reaching failure states. Among the 12 unrepaired columns, three exhibited the most promising values and were selected as control samples. Data were recorded through a computer system connected to the testing machine.

E. Test Setup and Column Instrumentation after Repair

Based on the data shown in Table II, the columns were sorted into four groups of MSF content: 0, 0.5, 2.0, and 2.5%. The addition of SNF to the mixture helped increase its strength from 20% to 60% [15]. Due to the influence of UHPFRC rheology, SF was limited to 6% of the content since when it exceeds a particular threshold (>10%), UHPFRC loses compression strength [16]. MSFs were added to the mix with varying contents of 0, 0.5, 2.0, and 2.5% and various aspect ratios of 28, 37, and 45, respectively, to enhance concrete properties. UHPFRC was used to reconstruct all the damaged columns using 30 mm thick jacket layers, as shown in Figure 6. To further monitor the compression strength of concrete in each mixture, concrete cubes and dogbone-shaped specimens were taken from the reinforced and repaired compositions.

TABLE II. MIXTURE PROPORTION FOR UHPFRC FOR 1 M³.

ID	Fiber (%)	W/C (-)	SNF (kg)	Sand (kg)	SP430 (kg)	SF (kg)	MSF (kg)	Water (kg)	Cement (kg)
M1	0.0	0.25	5	887	55	53	0.0	250	1000
M2	0.5	0.25	10	887	65	53	39.5	250	1000
M3	2.0	0.25	10	887	65	53	158	250	1000
M4	2.5	0.25	10	887	65	53	197.5	250	1000

Fig. 5. Testing of concrete columns until 90% load compression damage.

Fig. 6. Casting a square column with repaired material.

Based on the test variables shown in Table III, the columns were sorted into five groups. The first group (Co 0) was prepared from the normal concrete mix (M 0) and the three best of the 12 unrepaired columns were chosen as control specimens. In the second group (Co 1), three columns were strengthened with MSF-free UHPRC jacketing to study its effect on column behavior. In the rest of the groups (Co 2, Co

3, and Co 4), three columns in each group were strengthened by UHPFRC jacketing with MSF content of 0.5, 2.0, and 2.5% to study its effect on columns' behavior. All mixed groups were used to cast the column damage and the 100-mm cube. Columns and cubes were cured in water for 28 days and then kept in air at room temperature until the test day. All repaired specimens with UHPFRC were tested under axial compression with a displacement rate of 1 mm/min, as recommended in [17], until cracks appeared and the specimens failed, as shown in Figure 7. The average of the three-column specimens was considered during the loading process. Axial load and vertical displacement data were recorded through a computer system connected to the machine, and then the vertical load-displacement curve was plotted, which led to the determination of the ultimate load, displacement, and ductility. The crack patterns and the failure modes were determined throughout the experiment.

TABLE III. COLUMNS' DETAILS AND TEST VARIABLES

Group ID	Column ID	Concrete mix	Strengthening layer	Test variables
Co 0	Co 01	M0	None	The best value without strengthening
	Co 02			
	Co 03			
Co 1	Co 11	M1	0.0 % MSFs	Jacketing strengthening
	Co 12			
	Co 13			
Co 2	Co 21	M2	0.5 % MSFs	Content of MSF jacketing strengthening
	Co 22			
	Co 23			
Co 3	Co 31	M3	2.0 % MSFs	
	Co 32			
	Co 33			
Co 4	Co 41	M4	2.5 % MSFs	
	Co 42			
	Co 43			

Fig. 7. Testing of concrete column damage after using the repaired material.

III. TEST RESULTS

A. Concrete Properties

Table IV summarizes the properties of concrete mixes with and without UHPFRC jacketing. Compressive strength was obtained by testing three standard test cubes (100×100×100 mm) at the end of 28 days. The increase in MSF content in repair concrete also led to increased tensile and compressive strengths (f_{tu} and f_{cu}). At the testing date, after 28 days from casting, the f_{tu} and f_{cu} of M 0 for reinforcement concrete were 37.3 MPa and 2.41 Mpa, respectively. Since the MSF content

included in the UHPFRC was 0, 0.5, 2.0, and 2.5%, the compressive strength increased by 147.7, 169.1, 218.49, and 193.03%, respectively. These results corroborate previous studies [18-21]. However, compressive strength was observed to increase with MSF content of 0.5-2.0%, while it slightly decreased when using more than 2%. Therefore, the addition of MSF only to a certain extent increases the compressive strength [22]. In contrast, tensile strength is considered the most important feature of UHPFRC because the tensile strength in a cementitious repair material is important to avoid or reduce shrinkage deformations at an early stage. In this study, dogbone-shaped specimens were used to obtain tensile strength by testing all the mixtures at 28 days, as shown in Figure 8. Table IV shows that tensile strength increased by 125.9, 142.3, 190.80, and 202.7%, which was higher than the increase in compressive strength, while this increase might help close concrete cracks [23-25]. In [26], it was reported that using 1% or less steel fibers enhanced the properties of the concrete in general.

TABLE IV. COMPRESSIVE AND TENSILE STRENGTH OF CONCRETE WITH AND WITHOUT JACKETING

Mix ID	MSF (%)	f_{cu} (MPa)	μ_{cu} (%)	f_{tu} (MPa)	μ_{tu} (%)
M 0	0	37.3	-	3.59	-
M 1	0	55.1	147.7	4.52	125.9
M 2	0.5	63.1	169.1	5.11	142.3
M 3	2.0	81.5	218.49	6.85	190.80
M 4	2.5	72	193.03	7.28	202.7

f_{cu} = compressive strength, f_{tu} = tensile strength, μ_{cu} = ratio of compressive strength of any mix and mix 0, μ_{tu} = ratio of tensile strength

group, which had 2.0% MSF, showed the highest load capacity, since it increased by 165.7% compared to the unstrengthened columns (Co 0). According to [27], an increase in the volume of polyethylene fibers from 1% to 2% led to an increase in the maximum compressive load. Table V shows that the columns strengthened without MSF showed lower load capacities. Jacketing with 2.5% MSF had a trivial 15.9% decrease in column capacity compared to the column jacketed with 2% MSF. This shows that increasing the steel fiber by more than 2.0% of the volume will less effectively hold the microcracks in concrete and, consequently, have less loading capacity [22].

Fig. 8. Experimental tensile test of dogbones.

B. Load Capacity and Failure Mode of Columns

Table V shows the experimental results of the columns tested in terms of maximum load (P_u), failure modes, and displacement. The loading efficiency of the columns without strengthening by jacketing was calculated from:

$$(\mu_u \text{ average} = \frac{P_{u, \text{str average}}}{P_{u, \text{cc average}}}) \quad (1)$$

In general, all jacketed columns showed higher maximum load capacities than the unstrengthened (Co 0). The Co 3

In terms of failure mode, unstrengthened specimens cast with normal concrete (Co 0) were crushed (CC), as shown in Figure 9(a). In general, Figure 9(b)-(e) shows that the failure modes of the strengthened columns by UHPFRC jacketing showed concrete crushing (CC) followed by Steel Buckling (SB). On the contrary, including MSF at 0.5%, 2.0%, and 2.5% content, the failure pattern improved due to the increased load capacity of the specimens compared to the corresponding column cast with M 0. Figure 9(d) shows that the use of 2.0% instead of 2.5% MSF had a trivial effect on the maximum column load by creating smaller cracks, as the column failed on the strengthened portion. The reason may be that the effect of increasing the MSF was limited to a certain percentage, which would be less useful when exceeded.

TABLE V. CONCRETE PROPERTIES AND COLUMNS EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS.

Group ID	Column ID	f_{cu} (Mpa)	μI (%)	f_{tu} (Mpa)	$\mu 2$ (%)	P_u (kN)	average P_u (kN)	average μ_u (%)	Failure modes
Co 0	Co 01	37.3	-	3.59	-	472.0	446.6	-	Crushing (CC)
	Co 02					453.0			
	Co 03					415.0			
Co 1	Co 11	55.1	147.7	4.52	125.9	490.4	506.5	113.4	Crushing (CC) and Buckling (SB)
	Co 12					498.6			
	Co 13					530.6			
Co 2	Co 21	63.1	169.1	5.11	142.3	599.0	616.8	138.0	Crushing (CC) and Buckling (SB)
	Co 22					643.4			
	Co 23					608.0			
Co 3	Co 31	81.5	218.49	6.85	190.8	767.9	740.3	165.7	Crushing (CC) and Buckling (SB)
	Co 32					747.4			
	Co 33					706.5			
Co 4	Co 41	72.0	193.03	7.28	202.7	660.6	669.0	149.8	Crushing (CC) and Buckling (SB)
	Co 42					657.7			
	Co 43					688.8			

Fig. 9. Failure modes of the tested columns.

Fig. 10. Load-displacement curves of the tested columns: (a) M0, (b) M1, (c) M2, (d) M3, and (e) M4.

C. Load-Displacement and Ductility Behavior

Figure 10 shows the experimental load-displacement behavior of the tested columns. Figure 10(a) shows that the M1

jacketed columns showed higher initial displacements, averaging up to 72.41% of the Co 0 column's displacement. Table VI shows that the displacement and ductility of the

columns strengthened with UHPFRC jackets surpassed those of Co 0 from initial loading until failure. This can be attributed to the UHPFRC jacketing layer, which temporarily constrained and delayed lateral deformation. Moreover, MSF increased the displacement and ductility of the column, regardless of the MSF content, as shown in Figures 10(b-e). This means that it improved the column's stiffness until its maximum load and increased its ductility until the maximum load reached failure. The three columns strengthened by UHPFRC jacketing with 2.0% MSF (Co 31, Co 32, and Co 33), showed higher stiffness through increased displacement compared to all the other

strengthened columns. This could be because the increase in MSF content led to increased lateral deformation and column ductility [28]. Therefore, repairing with UHPFRC would restore the load-bearing capacity of concrete [29]. On the contrary, Table VI shows that Co 4 showed a lower average displacement and ductility than Co 3 by 7.54% and 4.16%, respectively, despite the increase in MSF. This could be because increasing the steel fiber content by more than 2.0% of the volume will be less effective in decreasing lateral deformation and helping to arrest the column cracking.

TABLE VI. LOAD-DISPLACEMENT AND DUCTILITY COLUMNS EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Group ID	Column ID	P_u (kN)	Average P_u (kN)	Δ_{yield} (mm)	Average Δ_{yield} (mm)	Δ_{ult} (mm)	Average Δ_{ult} (mm)	Ductility index μ	Average Ductility Index μ
Co 0	Co 01	472.0	446.6	2.90	2.67	3.1	2.9	1.07	1.10
	Co 02	453.0		1.80		2.1		1.17	
	Co 03	415.0		3.32		3.5		1.06	
Co 1	Co 11	490.4	506.5	4.39	4.32	5.2	5.0	1.20	1.16
	Co 12	498.6		3.10		3.4		1.11	
	Co 13	530.6		5.47		6.5		1.18	
Co 2	Co 21	599.0	616.8	5.72	4.73	5.72	5.1	1.05	1.17
	Co 22	643.4		4.80		4.80		1.26	
	Co 23	608.0		3.67		3.67		1.21	
Co 3	Co 31	767.9	740.3	4.82	4.60	6.3	5.7	1.32	1.25
	Co 32	747.4		4.53		6.1		1.35	
	Co 33	706.5		4.45		4.7		1.10	
Co 4	Co 41	660.6	669.0	4.17	4.36	5.2	5.3	1.26	1.20
	Co 42	657.7		4.92		6.1		1.25	
	Co 43	688.8		3.99		4.3		1.10	

IV. CONCLUSION

This study investigated 12 damaged reinforced concrete columns rehabilitated with a UHPFRC jacketing layer at different MSF content under axial compression loads, drawing the following conclusions:

- The use of UHPFRC led to enhanced concrete properties, notably increased compressive and tensile strengths, surpassing those of traditional RC, and was consistent with previous studies.
- All columns strengthened through UHPFRC jacketing, either with or without MSFs, showed higher maximum load capacities of up to 65.76% compared to unstrengthened columns.
- The use of MSF in the UHPFRC mixture to repair damaged columns resulted in improved concrete properties and increased column capacity. An optimal steel fiber content threshold of around 2.0% volume fraction was shown to achieve the maximum load-bearing capacity of the column, conforming with previous works mentioning that 2% is the ideal steel fiber content in concrete.
- Columns strengthened by jacketing with 2.0% MSF UHPFRC showed higher stiffness, load capacity, displacement, and ductility in comparison to the unstrengthened and the other strengthened columns. Furthermore, all jacketing layers (30 mm) increased column capacities and stiffness to the point of maximum loads, subsequently improving column ductility.

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REFERENCES

- [1] B. A. Tayeh, M. A. Naja, S. Shihada, and M. Arafa, "Repairing and Strengthening of Damaged RC Columns Using Thin Concrete Jacketing," *Advances in Civil Engineering*, vol. 2019, Jun. 2019, Art. no. e2987412, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/2987412>.
- [2] P. A. Calderón, J. M. Adam, S. Ivorra, F. J. Pallarés, and E. Giménez, "Design strength of axially loaded RC columns strengthened by steel caging," *Materials & Design*, vol. 30, no. 10, pp. 4069–4080, Dec. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2009.05.014>.
- [3] P. Sukontasukkul, P. Nimityongskul, and S. Mindess, "Effect of loading rate on damage of concrete," *Cement and Concrete Research*, vol. 34, no. 11, pp. 2127–2134, Nov. 2004, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconres.2004.03.022>.
- [4] K. Fukuyama, Y. Higashibata, and Y. Miyauchi, "Studies on repair and strengthening methods of damaged reinforced concrete columns," *Cement and Concrete Composites*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 81–88, Feb. 2000, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0958-9465\(99\)00044-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0958-9465(99)00044-X).
- [5] M. Yaqub and C. G. Bailey, "Repair of fire damaged circular reinforced concrete columns with FRP composites," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 359–370, Jan. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2010.06.017>.
- [6] P. Rossi, "Ultra-High Performance Fiber-Reinforced Concretes," *Concrete International*, vol. 23, no. 12, pp. 46–52, Dec. 2001.
- [7] G. Campione, M. Fossetti, C. Giacchino, and G. Minafo, "RC columns externally strengthened with RC jackets," *Materials and Structures*, vol. 47, no. 10, pp. 1715–1728, Oct. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1617/s11527-013-0146-x>.
- [8] M. K. Elsamny, M. K. Abd-Elhamed, H. A. Ezz-Eldeen, and A. A. Elmokranly, "Strengthening of eccentrically loaded rectangular

- reinforced concrete columns using steel wire mesh," *Civil Engineering Research Magazine (CERM)*, vol. 36, no. 4, pp. 226–247, 2014.
- [9] S. Abbas, M. L. Nehdi, and M. A. Saleem, "Ultra-High Performance Concrete: Mechanical Performance, Durability, Sustainability and Implementation Challenges," *International Journal of Concrete Structures and Materials*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 271–295, Sep. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40069-016-0157-4>.
- [10] E. Brühwiler and E. Denarié, "Rehabilitation and Strengthening of Concrete Structures Using Ultra-High Performance Fibre Reinforced Concrete," *Structural Engineering International*, vol. 23, no. 4, pp. 450–457, Nov. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.2749/101686613X13627347100437>.
- [11] A. Meda, G. A. Plizzari, and Z. R. & G. Martinola, "Strengthening of R/C existing columns with high performance fiber reinforced concrete jacket," in *Concrete Repair, Rehabilitation and Retrofitting II*, Boca Ration, FL, USA: CRC Press, 2008, pp. 443–448.
- [12] "Kingsun Chemicals for Concrete - Leading Manufacturer in China," *Kingsun Chemicals*. <https://kingsunchemical.com/>.
- [13] "ACI 318-08: Building Code Requirements for Structural Concrete and Commentary," American Concrete Institute, Farmington Hills, MI, USA, 2008.
- [14] "Designing Buildings - The construction wiki." <https://www.designingbuildings.co.uk>.
- [15] M. Z. A. M. Zahid, B. H. A. Bakar, and F. M. Nazri, "Behaviour of Post Heated Reinforced Concrete Columns," *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, vol. 244, no. 1, Oct. 2019, Art. no. 012006, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/244/1/012006>.
- [16] C. D. Smith, E. F. Jones, and M. D. Furnish, "Load-cycling in cubic press," *Shock Compression of Condensed Matter*, vol. 620, pp. 651–654, 2001.
- [17] M. Yaqub and C. G. Bailey, "Cross sectional shape effects on the performance of post-heated reinforced concrete columns wrapped with FRP composites," *Composite Structures*, vol. 93, no. 3, pp. 1103–1117, Feb. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2010.09.012>.
- [18] A. Meda, S. Mostosi, Z. Rinaldi, and P. Riva, "Corroded RC columns repair and strengthening with high performance fiber reinforced concrete jacket," *Materials and Structures*, vol. 49, no. 5, pp. 1967–1978, May 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1617/s11527-015-0627-1>.
- [19] "Recommendations for the tailoring of UHPFRC recipes for rehabilitation - Assessment and Rehabilitation of Central European Highway Structures," MCS/EU, Lausanne/Brussels, Deliverable D06, 2009.
- [20] A. Hussein, Z. M. R. A. Rasoul, and A. J. Alsaad, "Steel Fiber Addition in Eco-Friendly Zero-Cement Concrete: Proportions and Properties," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 9276–9281, Oct. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5178>.
- [21] N. A. Memon, M. A. Memon, N. A. Lakho, F. A. Memon, M. A. Keerio, and A. N. Memon, "A Review on Self Compacting Concrete with Cementitious Materials and Fibers," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 2969–2974, Jun. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2006>.
- [22] L. Vairagade and V. M. Bhedi, "Comparison of strength between steel fiber reinforced concrete and conventional concrete," *Track*, vol. 3, pp. 5–10, 2015.
- [23] H. Vikan and H. Justnes, "Rheology of cementitious paste with silica fume or limestone," *Cement and Concrete Research*, vol. 37, no. 11, pp. 1512–1517, Nov. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconres.2007.08.012>.
- [24] K. Wille, S. El-Tawil, and A. E. Naaman, "Properties of strain hardening ultra high performance fiber reinforced concrete (UHP-FRC) under direct tensile loading," *Cement and Concrete Composites*, vol. 48, pp. 53–66, Apr. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconcomp.2013.12.015>.
- [25] B. H. A. Bakar, A. T. Noaman, and H. M. Akil, "Cumulative Effect of Crumb Rubber and Steel Fiber on the Flexural Toughness of Concrete," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1345–1352, Feb. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.854>.
- [26] N. S. Kuyumar and T. Jaya Krishna, "A study for effect of steel fibre on strength of conventional concrete," *Materials Today: Proceedings*, vol. 62, pp. 3355–3360, Jan. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2022.04.249>.
- [27] A. Gholampour, R. Hassanli, J. E. Mills, T. Vincent, and M. Kunieda, "Experimental investigation of the performance of concrete columns strengthened with fiber reinforced concrete jacket," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 194, pp. 51–61, Jan. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2018.10.236>.
- [28] M. B. Eide and J.-M. Hisdal, "Ultra high performance fibre reinforced concrete (UHPFRC)–State of the art," SINTER Building and Infrastructure, Oslo, Norway, Coin Project Report 44, 2012.
- [29] M. Khairunnisa, C. Y. Yew, A. Z. M. Z. Affandi, Z. N. Zaiha, I. N. Fitriah, and Y. Norhaizura, "Study on the potential of using HPFRC as a repair material for concrete damaged RC short columns," in *AIP Conference Proceedings*, Nov. 2018, vol. 2030, Art. no. 020226, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5066867>.